

Finite Element Analysis for the Free Vibration of a Rigid Pavement resting on a Non-uniform Elastic Foundation

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a finite element analysis of the free vibration behavior of rigid pavements resting on non-uniform foundations. The rigid pavement was modeled using the Mindlin plate theory, while the supporting soil medium was approximated by a Winkler model with non-uniform stiffness. A finite element formulation was established to govern the equation of free vibration for rigid pavements. Subsequently, a computer program was developed based on the proposed algorithm, enabling the determination of natural frequencies and mode shapes. The accuracy of the proposed method was verified by comparing numerical examples of free vibration with analytical results. These numerical examples also demonstrate the significant influence of the foundation stiffness on natural frequencies and mode shapes.

Keywords-rigid pavement; FEM; free vibration; nonuniform foundation

I. INTRODUCTION

Rigid pavements offer numerous advantages, such as durability, longevity, good resistance to adverse environmental conditions [1], heavy load-bearing capacity, and high cycle fatigue durability. These qualities make them a suitable choice for airports and roads with heavy loads or high traffic density. Despite their outstanding characteristics, rigid pavements also have some drawbacks during operation. Except for continuously reinforced concrete pavements, rigid pavements contain joints to accommodate the expansion and contraction of concrete caused by temperature variations. The purpose of these joints is to prevent the development of curling and warping stresses in the slab, which can cause cracks or other forms of damage. Additionally, joints are often included due to limitations in construction technology. The arrangement of the transverse joints can cause uneven vehicle movement and generate noise. Furthermore, when joint sealing compounds

age, stormwater can infiltrate the foundation or subgrade, potentially altering the physical-mechanical properties of the base materials and/or subgrade soil. Consequently, this can cause a non-uniform load-bearing capacity of the foundation. Focussing on the noise defect of rigid pavements it can be assumed that their high stiffness and the presence of transverse joints result in greater noise emissions compared to other pavement types. The process of noise emission on the pavement is complicated and derives from numerous sources. However, it is partially attributed to the vibration of the pavement slabs and the interaction between the tire and the pavement surface. The analysis of foundation-supported structures has long been a popular topic in construction. Various types of structures have attracted interest, including beams on elastic foundations [2-4], beams on viscoelastic foundations, plates on elastic foundations [5-6], and plates on viscoelastic foundations [7-9]. Pavement slabs can be modeled as either thin or thick structures. Depending on the type of

problem, the analysis of plate structures can employ various methods including analytical approaches [10-11], semi-analytic techniques, numerical methods such as finite element analysis [3, 12-15], and isogeometric analysis [16-17]. In [18], the dynamic responses of pavement slabs resting on foundations were studied using a state space approach. In [19], the eigenproblems of plates with variable thicknesses supported by non-uniform elastic foundations were investigated using the element-free Galerkin method. In [20], Fourier and Laplace transforms were employed to solve the dynamic problems of concrete pavements subjected to impact loading. In [21], a trigonometric series approximation was used to determine the displacement of rectangular thick plates on the Pasternak foundation with free boundary edges. In [22], the crack behavior of cement concrete pavements was analyzed using the finite element software ILLI-SLAB. In [23], three-dimensional finite element analysis was used to study the dynamics of rigid pavements under moving loads.

Although several studies explored rigid pavements supported by elastic non-foundation, this study aims to develop a practical model applicable to engineers' design practices. Finite element formulations were developed for analyzing rigid pavements resting on non-uniform elastic foundations. The current analysis employed four-node quadrilateral elements and utilized displacement field assumptions based on the Mindlin plate theory. MATLAB was used to implement and execute the algorithms.

II. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL FOR RIGID PAVEMENT ON THE NONUNIFORM FOUNDATION

The model was a rigid pavement slab placed on a foundation, which includes layers of base/subbase and subgrade and exhibits non-uniform stiffness. This configuration is represented as a plate resting on a Winkler foundation, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Model of pavement slab on elastic foundation.

The computation incorporates the displacement field based on the first-order plate theory, commonly referred to as the Mindlin plate theory [24]:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= z\theta_x(x, y) \\ v(x, y, z) &= z\theta_y(x, y) \\ w(x, y, z) &= w_o(x, y) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where w_o represents the displacement along the z -axis, while θ_x and θ_y denote the rotations of the normal to the middle plane around the y and x axes, respectively.

Fig. 2. The rotations θ_x and θ_y in the Mindlin plate theory.

The strain formulation can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = z \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \theta_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \theta_y}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

$$\{\gamma\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \theta_x + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \\ \theta_y + \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

The stress-strain relations can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{E}{1-\mu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mu & 0 \\ \mu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1-\mu}{2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \begin{bmatrix} \mu & 0 \\ 0 & \mu \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{6}$$

where the stiffness of the material constituents is:

$$[D]_b = \frac{E}{1-\mu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \mu & 0 \\ \mu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1-\mu}{2} \end{bmatrix} \tag{7}$$

$$[D]_s = \frac{E}{2(1+\mu)} \begin{bmatrix} \mu & 0 \\ 0 & \mu \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

The strain energy of the Mindlin slab is given as:

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \frac{1}{2} \int_V \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} & \epsilon_{yy} & \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} [D]_b \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \right) dV + \\ &\frac{1}{2} \int_V \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} & \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} [D]_s \begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} \right) dV \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The potential energy of the non-uniform foundation is expressed as:

$$U_F = \frac{1}{2} \int_V K_w w^2 dV \tag{10}$$

The interpolation functions [24-25] are used for the quadrilateral element:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_1(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 - \eta) \\
 N_2(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 - \eta) \\
 N_3(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 + \xi)(1 + \eta) \\
 N_4(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{1}{4}(1 - \xi)(1 + \eta)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

The displacement fields are approximated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_x^e &= N_1\theta_{x1}^e + N_2\theta_{x2}^e + N_3\theta_{x3}^e + N_4\theta_{x4}^e \\
 \theta_y^e &= N_1\theta_{y1}^e + N_2\theta_{y2}^e + N_3\theta_{y3}^e + N_4\theta_{y4}^e \\
 w_0^e &= N_1w_1^e + N_2w_2^e + N_3w_3^e + N_4w_4^e
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{12}$$

Fig. 3. Quadrilateral element in natural coordinates.

The displacement vector at the *i*-th node is represented as:

$$\{u_i^e\} = \begin{Bmatrix} w_0^e \\ \theta_x^e \\ \theta_y^e \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{13}$$

Approximate strain is obtained using nodal displacements:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} w_0 \\ \theta_x \\ \theta_y \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{14}$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \gamma_{xz} \\ \gamma_{yz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} w_0 \\ \theta_x \\ \theta_y \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{15}$$

$$w = [N \quad 0 \quad 0] \begin{Bmatrix} w_0 \\ \theta_x \\ \theta_y \end{Bmatrix}
 \tag{16}$$

The bending strain stiffness matrix is defined as:

$$B_m = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} & 0 \end{bmatrix}
 \tag{17}$$

The shear strain stiffness matrix is given by:

$$B_s = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} \\ 0 & \frac{\partial N}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix}
 \tag{18}$$

Element stiffness matrices for bending in rigid pavements are:

$$K_m = \int_{\Omega} B_m^T [D]_b B_m d\Omega
 \tag{19}$$

The element stiffness matrices for shear in rigid pavements are:

$$K_s = \int_{\Omega} B_s^T [D]_s B_s d\Omega
 \tag{20}$$

The element stiffness matrices for the elastic foundation are:

$$K_f = \int_{\Omega} B_f^T K_w B_f d\Omega
 \tag{21}$$

The stiffness matrices of the elements are:

$$K^e = K_m + K_s + K_f
 \tag{22}$$

The element mass matrices are:

$$M^e = \int_{\Omega} \begin{bmatrix} N & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} m_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} N & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N \end{bmatrix} d\Omega
 \tag{23}$$

The forced vibration equation is given by:

$$[M]\{\ddot{U}\} + [K]\{U\} = \{F\}
 \tag{24}$$

where *K*, *U*, and *F* represent the stiffness, displacement, and load matrices, respectively. The free vibration equation is expressed as:

$$[M]\{\ddot{U}\} + [K]\{U\} = \{0\}
 \tag{25}$$

The displacement is represented in terms of a harmonic function, given as:

$$\{U\} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_{ne} \end{Bmatrix} \sin(\omega t + \varphi)
 \tag{26}$$

By substituting (26) into (25), an eigenvalue problem can be derived to determine the natural frequencies:

$$([K] - \omega^2[M])\{U\} = \{0\}
 \tag{27}$$

III. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A. Example 1: Validation examples

The natural frequencies of a simply supported rectangular plate on an elastic foundation obtained with the proposed method were compared with the exact analytical results derived using an analytical method [27]. A simply supported rectangular plate was considered, with *a* = 2 m, *b* = 2 m, thickness *h* = 0.12 m, and elastic modulus *E* = 30 GPa, mass density $\rho = 2400\text{kg/m}^3$, and Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.25$. The plate was discretized into a grid of 10x10 finite elements. The equivalent stiffness of the foundation is defined as:

$$k_F = \frac{K_0 a^4}{E h^3}
 \tag{28}$$

Table I presents the computed results of the rigid pavement natural frequencies using the proposed method. A comparison with the exact solutions obtained by an analytical method [27] revealed very small differences, all less than 0.4%. Figure 4 visualizes modes 1 and 2.

Fig. 4. (a) First and (b) second mode shapes.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF PROPOSED METHODS' RESULTS WITH EXTRACT SOLUTION

k_F	Mode	Natural frequencies (rad/s)		
		Present	Analytical method [27]	Error (%)
1	Mode 1	280.6415	281.4026	0.2705
	Mode 2	692.5564	695.1653	0.3753
5	Mode 1	296.0160	296.7765	0.2563
	Mode 2	698.9040	701.5295	0.3743
10	Mode 1	314.1780	314.9404	0.2421
	Mode 2	706.7583	709.4045	0.3730
20	Mode 1	347.6671	348.4389	0.2215
	Mode 2	722.2106	724.8979	0.3707

B. Example 2

To investigate the impact of a non-uniform foundation on the free vibration of a rigid pavement, a slab with dimensions $a = 3$ m, $b = 4$ m, and a thickness of 16 cm was considered. This slab was characterized by an elastic modulus $E = 30$ Gpa and a Poisson's coefficient of 0.25. The boundary condition of the rigid pavement plate consists of four free edges. The stiffness of the non-uniform elastic foundation is assumed as follows:

Foundation 1: linear variation:

$$K_F = K_0 \left(1 + \gamma \frac{x}{a} + \lambda \frac{y}{b} \right) \tag{29}$$

Foundation 2: nonlinear variation:

$$K_F = K_0 \left\{ 1 + \gamma \left(0.5 - \frac{x}{a} \right)^2 + \lambda \left(0.5 - \frac{y}{b} \right)^2 \right\} \tag{30}$$

The parameters for the non-uniform foundation were assumed as $k_F = 10$, $\gamma = 0.4$, $\lambda = 0.4$. Figure 5 illustrates the

first three mode shapes of a simply supported pavement plate on a non-uniform linear elastic foundation, with stiffness parameter $k_F = 10$. Figure 5(b),(c) shows the loss of asymmetry in the mode shapes due to the nonuniform stiffness of the foundation.

Fig. 5. Modes (a) 1, (b) 2, and (c) 3 with linear elastic foundation $k_F = 10$.

Table II depicts the calculated results of the first three natural frequencies for a simply supported pavement plate on a foundation, considering two types of non-uniform foundations: linear and nonlinear. Numerical analysis reveals that the frequencies associated with a linearly varying foundation were higher compared to those associated with a quadratic variation.

TABLE II. NATURAL FREQUENCIES OF RIGID PAVEMENT ON NONUNIFORM FOUNDATION

k_F		Natural frequencies (rad/s)		
		Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3
1	Foundation 1	223.47	454.17	634.24
	Foundation 2	221.61	453.29	633.62
10	Foundation 1	279.03	483.90	655.83
	Foundation 2	263.81	475.62	649.75
20	Foundation 1	329.90	514.93	678.98
	Foundation 2	303.90	499.26	667.22

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a finite element formulation for analyzing the free vibration behavior of a rigid pavement resting on a non-uniform elastic foundation. The stiffness of the non-uniform elastic foundation was assumed to exhibit linear or quadratic variation within the rigid pavement plane. MATLAB was employed to implement and execute the algorithms developed for computing the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the free vibrations. The numerical results clearly illustrated that the mode shape of the vibration undergoes significant changes when the foundation stiffness varies.

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Analysis of a Compact Electrically Small Antenna with SRR for RFID Applications

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ABSTRACT

This paper contains the design and analysis of a compact, bidirectional Electrically Small Antenna (ESA) at 0.9 GHz for Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and a global system for mobile communication applications. The proposed design consists of a microstrip patch antenna enclosed inside the split ring resonators, in which a split ring resonator was subtracted from the ground plane in order to obtain the results at lower frequencies by maintaining a compact size. This ESA was designed on FR4 substrate having a dimension of 30 mm × 30 mm × 1.6 mm. This antenna was created and simulated with the Ansys HFSS. The ESA was fabricated by chemical etching and it was measured with the MS2037C Anritsu Combinational Analyzer. The simulated results show that the ESA attains a bandwidth of 100 MHz (with S11 < -10 dB) at 0.9 GHz. The bidirectional radiation pattern in both H and E planes with a radiation efficiency of 80% at the resonant frequency was obtained. A close agreement of 90% between the simulated and the measured results was observed.

Keywords-electrically small antenna; microstrip patch; SRR; RFID applications

I. INTRODUCTION

Systems for Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) frequently employ microstrip antennas. Such systems have a wide range of practical uses in business, trade, transportation, biological research and clinical practice [1, 2]. An antenna and an RFIC are the only components of a passive tag. The devices that are designed by utilizing surface acoustic waves may be employed in wireless sensing applications (such as distance, temperature etc.) [3]. Most popularly available RFID tags for

UHF and RF applications are designed with the help of electrically small antennas or standard half-wavelength planar dipole antennas [2, 4]. Implanted microwave technology is becoming more and more common for medical purposes [5, 6]. The electromagnetic signal degrades because of the medium around the implanted device has a high ϵ_r and a high δ . Due to the reduction of the dielectric medium properties effect, magnetic connection between the tag loop and the reader loop is preferred in this situation [6]. The loop dimensions employed inside biological media is often small, that is less than $\lambda/2$.

According to the third degree of the source's distance, the magnetic field dramatically decreases in the near-field zone [7]. To pick up a weakly backscattered response from the destination point, the microstrip antenna being used as a reader must provide a strong magnetic field. Typically, to do that, the microstrip patch dimensions must be increased. Building the patch as a periodically loaded line in order to realize an electrically small antenna is proposed in this paper. Between each leg of the loop, capacitors are routinely put as part of the line's architecture. The loop's electrical length is shortened as a result of the capacitive components' compensation for the phase incursion given by the inductive portions. The increased magnetic coupling is followed by a homogenous current distribution around the loop in this arrangement [8, 9]. To raise the tag read range while employing an ESA in the far-field area, the base station ESA should have superior radiation properties. ESAs are known to exhibit omnidirectional radiation in the loop plane. The reader antenna is intended to be built using an antenna module that combines a dipole with a non-interacting electrically small antenna. Additionally, this antenna's gain is twice as great as the gains of a single patch or single dipole antenna [9, 10]. The ESA is also small, which makes it useful for portable RFID scanners that communicate with conventional passive tags. In order to arbitrarily change the resonant frequency of a bowtie dipolar tag, the idea of integrating an inductive channel with a lumped external inductor was introduced in [25]. It was demonstrated that the inductive channel could readily control the currents flowing on the top-loading patch, and that channel width and an external lumped inductor could both be changed to efficiently alter the tag antenna's resonance frequency. The tag antenna, which has a two-layer construction and a high profile, cannot be read in all polarizations. A metal-mountable tag with many frequency tuning options has been created using two complementary C-shaped patches in [26]. The two patches are in close proximity in order to produce enough antenna reactance [27-28].

An ESA with a bidirectional radiation pattern for UHF RFID applications is proposed in this study. An SRR structure was utilized to minimize the size. The simulated results indicate that the electrically small antenna achieves bidirectional radiation pattern. There were no observable effects to the proposed antenna's resonance frequency, gain, and radiation pattern when they were stacked or tiled together.

II. ANTENNA DESIGN GEOMETRY

A. Methodology

The configuration and dimensions of the compact ESA are represented in Figure 1. It consists of a microstrip patch enclosed with SRRs in which a tile of microstrip transmission lines was subtracted from the microstrip patch. The microstrip ESA is engraved on FR4 material with 1.6 mm thickness and $\tan\delta = 0.02$. In addition to that, an SRR was subtracted from the ground plane with a dimension of 30 mm x 30 mm printed on the backside of the substrate. The complete geometry of the antenna is 30 mm x 30 mm x 1.6 mm and an impedance of 50 Ω is attached to the microstrip patch as excitation. The microstrip ESA with SRR was designed and simulated in Ansys HFSS and the properties of the material are represented

in Table I. The dimensions utilized in designing the microstrip patch antenna are shown in Table II.

Fig. 1. Microstrip ESA with SRR: (a) Front view, (b) back view.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES OF MICROSTRIP ESA WITH SRR

Parameter	Value	Unit
Patch	Copper	----
Thickness	1.6	mm
Density	8.96	gcm^{-3}
Electrical conductivity	58.7	siemens/m
Electrical resistivity	1.7	$\Omega\cdot\text{m}$
Thermal conductivity	386	W/m. K
Sheet resistance	0.5	$\text{m}\Omega/\text{sq}$
Substrate	FR4 epoxy	-
Thickness	0.1	mm
Dielectric constant (ϵ_r)	4.4	-

TABLE II. DIMENSIONS OF THE PROPOSED MICROSTRIP ESA WITH SRR

Dimension	Value (mm)
Width of the ground plane (W)	30
Length of the ground plane (L)	30
Length of the microstrip Patch (L_1)	21
Width of the microstrip Patch (W_1)	16
Length of the microstrip Patch (L_2)	14
Width of the microstrip Patch (W_2)	12
Length of the microstrip Patch (L_3)	2
Width of the microstrip Patch (W_3)	1

B. Evolution Procedure

Figure 2 represents the evolutionary stages of the electrically small microstrip patch antenna with SRR structure. Antenna evolution process starts with the design of an ESA fed

by a 50 Ω microstrip transmission line (step 1). A rectangle of 16 mm width and 21 mm length was subtracted from the microstrip patch. Subsequently, a 14 mm × 2 mm rectangle was united to the patch antenna (the step 2). In step 4, the proposed antenna was designed with a full ground structure. In step 5, the microstrip antenna with the SRR structure in the ground plane is complete.

Fig. 2. Microstrip ESA with SRR. (a) Step 1, (b) step 2, (c) step 3, (d) step 4, (e) proposed design.

The dimensions of the microstrip patch antenna were calculated by utilizing the concept behind the theory of the transmission lines. The width of the patch can be calculated by:

$$W = \frac{v_o}{2F_r} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\epsilon_r + 1}} \quad (1)$$

The length of the patch can be calculated by (2), where ϵ_{reff} is the effective dielectric constant of the substrate:

$$L = \frac{c}{2F_r \sqrt{\epsilon_{reff}}} - 2\Delta l \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta l = 0.412h \frac{(\epsilon_{reff} + 0.03)(w + 0.26h)}{(\epsilon_{reff} - 0.258)(w + 0.8h)}$$

The dielectric constant of the substrate is:

$$\epsilon_{reff} = \frac{\epsilon_r + 1}{2} + \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{2} \left[1 + \left[\frac{12h}{w} \right] \right]^{-1/2} \quad (3)$$

where L and W are the length and width of the microstrip patch, h is the thickness of the FR4 substrate, v_o is the velocity of light in free space and F_r is the resonant frequency of the antenna.

Figure 3 represents the simulated S11 of the microstrip ESA with SRR at different evolutionary stages. At the first step, the basic microstrip patch resonates at 0.8 GHz with a reflection co-efficient of -10 dB. At the second stage ESA resonates at 0.82 GHz with a S11 of -10 dB. In the third step antenna resonates at 0.85 GHz with a S11 of -16 dB and in addition to that antenna resonates at 2.3 GHz with a S11 of -11 dB. In step 4, the antenna without the SRR resonates at 0.87 GHz with a return loss of -20 dB and an additional band has been obtained at 2.3 GHz with a return loss of -12 dB. The final proposed antenna resonates at 900 MHz with a return loss of -22 dB, with an additional band obtained at 2.3 GHz having a return loss of -13 dB. As we have designed an electrically small antenna, we were not concentrated at 2.3 GHz and that is why we are discussing the resonant frequency of the antenna at 900 MHz by maintaining the lower size.

Fig. 3. Simulated return loss of the microstrip ESA with SRR at different evolutionary stages.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation of the proposed microstrip ESA with SRR was done by using Ansys HFSSv13 based on Finite Element Method (FEM) and Method of Moments (MOM). The microstrip ESA with SRR was excited by using a microstrip transmission line having a characteristic impedance of 50 Ω. To verify the simulated results were accurate, the proposed microstrip ESA was fabricated by using FR4 material as represented in Figure 4. The antenna fabrication was done by using chemical etching while parameters like reflection coefficient and VSWR of the antenna were measured with the MS2037C Anritsu Combinational analyzer. Radiation pattern

and gain of the antenna were measured with an Anechoic Chamber by utilizing antenna measurement equipment. Figure 5 shows the fabricated antenna measured with the combinational analyzer. Figure 6 shows the simulated and fabricated reflection coefficient of the microstrip ESA with split ring resonators.

Fig. 4. Fabricated prototype of the Microstrip ESA with SRR.

Fig. 5. Measurement of the Microstrip ESA with SRR.

Fig. 6. Simulated and fabricated reflection coefficient of the Microstrip ESA with SRR.

From the return loss plot, it was observed that the simulated microstrip ESA with SRR resonates at 900 MHz with an S11 of -22 dB and the measured antenna resonates at 900 MHz with a reflection coefficient of -20 dB. Small deviation between the

simulated and fabricated results due to connector and cable losses was detected.

Fig. 7. Simulated and fabricated VSWR of the Microstrip ESA with SRR.

Fig. 8. Simulated and measured radiation pattern of the proposed ESA with SRR: (a) $\theta=0^\circ$, (b) $\theta=90^\circ$, (c) $\theta=180^\circ$.

Figure 7 shows the VSWR variation of the antenna with frequency. The proposed antenna resonates at 0.9 GHz. At the

resonant frequency, the simulated VSWR is 1.25 and the measured VSWR is 1.89. The radiation pattern was collected from an anechoic chamber employing antenna measurement equipment. A standard horn antenna is used as reference. Antenna efficiency of 80% is obtained by using the formula and selecting the values of incident and radiated power.

The radiation pattern is another significant antenna characteristic. Figures 8 and 9 demonstrate an antenna gain and the antenna radiation pattern. The minor variations between the fabricated and the simulated outcomes are caused by measurement and alignment issues.

Fig. 9. Simulated and measured azimuthal radiation pattern of the proposed ESA with SRR: (a) $\phi=0^\circ$, (b) $\phi=90^\circ$, (c) $\phi=180^\circ$.

The E-field and current distribution of an electrically tiny circular ring antenna are shown in Figure 10. Maximum radiation is indicated by the red color, minimum radiation is

indicated by the blue color, and the average distribution of surface currents is indicated by the green color. Figure 11 represents the measurement setup of the proposed antenna for measuring antenna parameters like gain and radiation pattern in an anechoic chamber. Figure 12 represents the 3D gain of the planar microstrip ESA with SRR.

Fig. 10. Vector current and H-field distribution of the proposed microstrip ESA with SRR.

Fig. 11. Measurement setup of gain and radiation pattern.

Table III compares several previously published in literature antennas to the proposed broadband antenna for RFID applications. When compared to the proposed antenna, the

antenna suggested in [4] offered modest return loss. The antenna in [6] is huge in size and has a constrained impedance bandwidth. The antenna in [8] has a straightforward design and it offers less return loss and VSWR. According to [13], the antenna occupies more size and featured a complicated construction printed in Taconic RF-35. The comparison displays that the proposed broadband antenna has a number of benefits over earlier reported antennas [4–13] in terms of size, impedance bandwidth, and gain.

Fig. 12. 3D gain of the proposed microstrip ESA with SRR.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED ANTENNA WITH OTHER KNOWN ANTENNAS

Ref.	Size (mm ³)	Material used	Resonant frequency	Return loss	VSWR
[24]	40×40×1.6	FR4	870 MHz	-10.1 dB	1.8
[25]	60×70×0.5	Rogers/RT Duroid 5880	890 MHz	-14 dB	1.89
[26]	50×50×0.8	FR4	900 MHz	-18 dB	1.78
[27]	40×40×1.5	Rogers/RT Duroid 5880	870 MHz	-12 dB	1.85
[28]	80×20×0.5	Taconic RF-35	1.7 GHz	-15 dB	1.55
Proposed	30×30×1.6	FR4	900 MHz	-22 dB	1.25

IV. CONCLUSION

A compact, bidirectional Electrically Small Antenna (ESA) resonating at 900 MHz was designed, simulated, and measured with the MS2037C Anritsu Combinational Analyzer and its simulated S11 is -22 dB at 900 MHz. The measured bandwidth S11 < -10 dB is 100 MHz. There is a good match between the simulated and the measured results in terms of VSWR and S11. Radiation pattern is bidirectional in both the azimuthal and elevation angles, thus, the proposed antenna is suitable for RFID applications and for mobile communication applications.

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The Effect of the Utilization of Sustainable Materials on Some Mechanical Properties of Geopolymer Mortar

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ABSTRACT

Geopolymer concrete has been developed as a means of reducing carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions due to concrete manufacturing, which account for around 5–10% of the total global CO₂ emissions. Additionally, this innovative material aims to utilize industrial waste as a sustainable resource. This study concentrates on developing a geopolymer mortar composition comprising 70% fly ash and 30% metakaolin. The mixture also includes 14 molars of sodium hydroxide, sodium silicate, saturated surface dry sand, water at a volume of 10% of the mix, and 1.5% superplasticizer. The solution-to-solid materials ratio was established at 0.55 while the ratio between sodium silicate and sodium hydroxide was established at 2.5:1. The geopolymer mortar was enhanced by rice husk fibers at varying volume percentages of 1%, 1.5%, and 2%. Additionally, waste paper, in the form of paper ash, was introduced as filler at a volume percentage of 5%. Following the demolding process, the specimens were cured in the controlled environment of an oven, with the temperature set at 60 °C for a period of 24 hr. Subsequently, the cured samples were stored for 7 and 28 days and then were tested. When different amounts of rice husk fibers were mixed in with a fixed amount of 5% paper ash, the flexural resistance of the geopolymer mortar increased significantly. After 7 days of curing, it was seen that the flexural strength experienced an increase of 4%, 13%, and 25%, and a further increase of 11%, 18%, and 31% after 28 days of curing. The results of the impact test showed a notable enhancement in impact resistance and energy absorption when incorporating paper ash and rice husk fibers. Specifically, the initial crack results exhibited a 50% rise, while the specimen failure after 28 days of curing showed a 66% improvement.

Keywords-geopolymer mortar; fly ash; metakaolin; rice husk fibers; waste paper ash; impact test; flexural strength

I. INTRODUCTION

The issues of global warming and pollution have emerged as significant challenges in contemporary times. The manufacture of Portland cement results in the emission of significant amounts of gases, leading to atmospheric pollution [1]. Concrete is extensively regarded as the primary construction material, with its utilization projected to escalate in line with global population growth, economic advancement, and the need for upkeep or replacement of aging infrastructure. Unfortunately, a primary constituent of the aforementioned material, which is cement, is accountable for approximately 5–10% of global CO₂ emissions. Consequently, there is a pressing need for a comprehensive reevaluation of both the industry as a whole and the particular material in question [2]. It is possible to minimize the CO₂ emissions due to cement production and contribute to the recycling of industrial wastes that have a

major effect on the environment by using sustainable materials in civil engineering projects [3]. The term geopolymer was introduced in 1978 to designate a group of mineral binders that demonstrate chemical characteristics similar to zeolites. Geopolymers, in contrast to conventional Portland cement, utilize the polycondensation process of silicon (Si) and aluminum (Al) precursors to generate the matrix and impart structural stability [4]. Geopolymers consist mostly of two essential components, namely source materials and alkaline solutions. The constituents required for the synthesis of alumina-silicate geopolymers should possess a substantial concentration of Si and Al. The minerals in question may be composed of naturally occurring substances such as kaolinite, clays, and similar compounds, characterized by empirical formulas that include Si, Al, and oxygen (O) [5]. The usage of slag, fly ash, rice husk, metakaolin, red mud, activated

bentonite clay, and other aluminosilicate minerals as the primary supply materials are imperative. Geopolymer cement is produced through the alkaline activation of the aforementioned raw components. The utilization of natural pozzolana is recommended for the production of geopolymers that are predominantly composed of aluminosilicate compounds. Alkaline liquids are obtained by soluble compounds of alkali metals, namely sodium or potassium. Sodium hydroxide, a caustic liquid, is commonly employed in conjunction with sodium silicate at a 2.5:1 ratio. Sodium is favored over potassium due to its comparatively cheaper cost [6]. The primary objective of this research is to investigate the flexural strength of fly ash-metakaolin geopolymer mortar reinforced with rice husk fibers and the effect of waste paper ash addition. This investigation target is to develop our understanding of the structural geopolymer mortar characteristics. It will also highlight the prospect of reducing CO₂ emissions by manufacturing environmentally friendly concrete through the application of sustainable and waste materials in place of traditional cement.

Authors in [7] investigated the impact of different amounts of slag as a potential substitute for fly ash while also assessing the influence of slag on geopolymer concrete characteristics. The ratios of slag to fly ash were 0.25:0.75, 0.35:0.65, and 0.45:0.55, expressed in terms of material weight. Subsequently, the aforementioned compositions were subjected to a comparative analysis with a reference mixture of conventional concrete, which adhered to a mix of 1:1.5:3 (Portland cement: natural sand: coarse aggregates), respectively. The utilization of copper fiber obtained from discarded electrical devices has been employed to improve the characteristics of geopolymer concrete. Curing was done by heat at a temperature of 40 °C. The findings of this study indicated that the combination of 45% slag and 55% fly ash yielded the most favorable outcome [7]. Authors in [8] employed a series of experimental combinations to produce geopolymer mortar incorporating 1% micro-steel fibers. In order to see how fly ash changed the properties of geopolymer mortar, different weight percentages of 50%, 60%, and 70% of the slag weight were used. Combining fly ash and slag in a 50:50 ratio with micro-steel fibers at 1% produced the most advantageous ratio that created the most notable results. The samples were subjected to an oven curing temperature of 240 °C for a duration of 4 hr. Fiber incorporation resulted in an increase in the compressive resistance of the geopolymer by 11%, 11.5%, and 14% after 3, 7, and 28 days of curing, respectively. Flexural resistance demonstrated enhanced rates of 28%, 30%, and 33%, respectively [8]. Authors in [9] aimed to investigate the impact of incorporating rice husk fibers at 1% of mix volume on the characteristics of Reactive Powder Concrete (RPC). The samples were oven cured at 60°C and tested after 28 days of curing. Based on the results, it was observed that the compressive strength of the RPC increased by 7.4%, while its dry density decreased by 0.69%. In contrast, the workability of the RPC exhibited a drop of 5.62% in comparison to the reference combination. Authors in [10] investigated the impact of including paper fibers on the characteristics of hardened and fresh concrete. The conducted tests indicate that the incorporation of waste paper into concrete leads to a substantial

enhancement in both compressive and flexural strength. After a curing time of 90 days, the compressive strength exhibited a notable rise of 34.21%, while the flexural strength demonstrated a substantial increase of 42.4%. In that study, waste paper comprised 1% of the total volume of concrete [10].

The most important goal of the current research is the environmental benefit of reducing CO₂ emissions from the cement production industry and produce cheaper concrete with high strength and quality. Therefore, this study explored the flexural strength and impact strength of fly ash-metakaolin geopolymer mortar. The possibility of utilizing rice husk as fibers and waste paper ash as filler, is highlighted since there are only a few published studies regarding this subject.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Fly Ash (FA)

Class-F FA was used. The classification of FA is determined according to the specifications outlined in ASTM C618-19, as depicted in Table I. The aforementioned category of FA exhibits pozzolanic characteristics [11].

TABLE I. CHEMICAL REQUIREMENTS OF FLY ASH

Oxide	Content, %	(ASTM C618-19) requirement
Fe ₂ O ₃	5.31	Total Sum. > 50%
Al ₂ O ₃	18	
SiO ₂	64.73	
SO ₃	0.25	Maximum 5%
MgO	0.87	--
CaO	2.3	Maximum 18%
K ₂ O	3.52	--
Na ₂ O	2.22	--
L.O.I	2.8	Maximum 6%

B. Metakaolin (MK)

Class N-metakaolin, a natural pozzolana, was used. It is categorized according to the specifications stated in ASTM C618-19, as indicated in Table II.

TABLE II. CHEMICAL REQUIREMENTS OF METAKAOLIN

Oxide	Content, %	(ASTM C618-19) requirement
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.93	Total sum. > 70%
Al ₂ O ₃	40.45	
SiO ₂	51.4	
SO ₃	0.32	Maximum 4%
MgO	0.47	--
CaO	2.3	Maximum 18%
K ₂ O	0.272	--
Na ₂ O	1.018	--
L.O.I	1.84	Maximum 10%

C. Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH)

A NaOH solution was prepared by adding distilled water to caustic soda flakes (99% purity). The variety of molar concentrations can be determined by considering the ratio between water and soda flakes. The NaOH solution is explained in greater detail in the ASTM E291-2009 standard. The concentration of NaOH utilized in this study is 14 mol/L [12].

D. Sodium Silicate (Na_2SiO_3)

The sodium silicate used in this study was made in the UAE, and its concentration was determined by calculating Na_2O to SiO_2 and H_2O ratios.

E. Water

The water used for mixing complied with IQS 1703-2018 [13].

F. Fine Aggregate (Sand)

In this investigation, sand was employed as the fine aggregate. It was classified as zone two and was found to be in accordance with the requirements specified in IQS (No. 45-2019), as demonstrated in Table III. The fineness modulus was 2.84 [13].

TABLE III. SIEVE ANALYSIS OF FINE AGGREGATE

Sieve no.	Accumulative passing %	IQS (45-2019), zone 2
10	100	100
4.75	96	90-100
2.36	84	75-100
1.18	69	55-90
0.6	50	35-59
0.3	15	8-30
0.15	2	0-10

G. Wastepaper Ash (PA)

The paper pieces were cut into small pieces with dimensions of 8 mm, 2 mm, and 0.1 mm. Subsequently, the specimens were burned in a furnace operating at 700 °C. The resulting residue was subjected to sieving using a 600 μm sieve. A 5% volume fraction of wastepaper ash was incorporated into the cementitious components. Table IV presents an overview of the chemical properties of wastepaper ash.

TABLE IV. CHEMICAL REQUIREMENTS OF WASTEPAPER ASH

Oxide	Content %
SiO_2	20
Al_2O_3	4.2
Fe_2O_3	0.76
CaO	78.74
MgO	0.88

The papers had been cut into small pieces with 8 mm, 2 mm, and 0.1 mm dimensions. Subsequently, the specimen was burned in a furnace operating at a temperature of 700°C. Following the process of burning, the resulting residue was subjected to sieving using a 600 μm sieve. A 5% volume fraction of ash wastepaper was incorporated into the cementitious components. Table IV presents an overview of the chemical properties of wastepaper ash.

H. Rice Husk Fibers (RHF)

Table V and Figure 1 show the length and other parameters of the RHF employed in this investigation.

TABLE V. RICE HUSK FIBERS MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Property	Value
Diameter (mm)	0.5
Length (mm)	5
Aspect ratio	10
Density kg/m^3	700
Color	Gold or hay

Fig. 1. Rice husk fibers.

I. Super Plasticizer (SP)

The research utilized BETONAC-1055, a substance supplied by the local region. It adheres to the ASTM C494 Type F standard and was employed for the purpose of enhancing the workability of the geopolymer mortar [14].

III. MANUFACTURING OF GEOPOLYMER MORTAR

A. Mixing

It is necessary to prepare the NaOH solution one day in advance of the intended mixing. The concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was established at a molarity of 14 M for the geopolymer mortar. The ratio of Na_2SiO_3 to NaOH was established at 2.5:1, whereas the ratio of the solution to cementitious material was determined at 0.55. In the first step of the mixing process, NaOH solution, Na_2SiO_3 , 1.5% superplasticizer, and 10% water (by weight of cementitious material) were mixed together. This mixture was blended for 2–5 min. Subsequently, the dry components, namely FA (70%), metakaolin (30%), and sand in a Saturated Surface Dry (SSD) state, were meticulously mixed manually for about 5 min. Therefore, 75% of the liquid components were included in the dry constituents and manually blended for an additional duration of 10–15 min. Following this, a resting period of 15 s took place prior to the addition of the remaining 25% of the liquid components, which were then mixed for an additional 10 min. Homogeneity was achieved after approximately 30 min of mixing. The paper ash was added at 5% for all mixes. The RHF and the wastepaper ashes were added at 1%, 1.5, and 2% by volume of the mixture. Table VI illustrates the mix design of geopolymer mortar.

TABLE VI. MIX PROPORTIONS OF GEOPOLYMER MORTAR FOR 1m³, WEIGHT IN Kg/m³

Mix	FA	Metakaolin	Sand	NaOH	Na ₂ SiO ₃	SP	RHF
GPr	287	123	1476	64	161	6.15	-
GP1	287	123	1476	64	161	6.15	1%
GP2	287	123	1476	64	161	6.15	1.5%
GP3	287	123	1476	64	161	6.15	2%

B. Curing

The specimens were oven-cured at 60 °C for 24 hr, followed by a transfer to a separate oven for cooling and temperature maintenance until the scheduled test date. As seen in Figures 2 and 3, the specimens were tested at 7 and 28 days. Elevated temperatures accelerate chemical reactions, promoting a more rapid solidification of the substance. The importance of this matter lies in construction projects. The 7-day age is indicative of the initial strength, whereas the 28-day age is widely accepted as the standard for assessing the material's intended long-term strength and durability.

Fig. 2. Geopolymer prisms while curing.

Fig. 3. Impact samples while curing.

C. Testing

1) Flexural Strength

The flexural strength of the geopolymer mortar was assessed by conducting a one-point load test, following the guidelines provided in ASTM C 293M-16. The flexural strength of each combination was measured using the average of two prism specimens (250 × 50 × 50 mm) after curing for 3 and 28 days [15].

D. Impact Test

As suggested by the ACI 544.2R-10 standard, a hardened steel ball with a diameter of 6.35 cm was dropped from a height of 1.5 m onto a 500 mm × 500 mm × 50 mm slab [16].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Geopolymers are a suitable, environmentally friendly alternative to Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) for use in structural applications [18].

A. Flexural Strength

The flexural strength test was performed after 7 and 28 days of curing at 60 °C. The samples included one without any fibers or paper ash and 3 samples with varying percentages (1%, 1.5%, and 2%) of fibers and 5% paper ash. The test results are illustrated in Table VII and Figures 4 and 5. The incorporation of RHF resulted in an improvement in flexural strength through the reduction of cracking. The initial cracks on the bending specimen were not easily seen due to the role of fibers as bridges between cracks which enhanced the strength of the fiber-reinforced concrete. These findings align with the conclusions presented in [9]. Furthermore, the addition of paper ash showed a significant upgrade in flexural tensile strength as the curing period progressed. The observed increase in gain can be attributed to the utilization of paper ash as a filler material, which effectively fills voids in concrete and consequently ameliorates its flexural strength. These findings are in accordance with the ones reported in [18].

TABLE VII. FLEXURAL STRENGTH TEST RESULTS

Mix	Flexural strength, MPa	
	7 days	28 days
GPr	4.15	4.43
GP1	4.32	4.9
GP2	4.7	5.24
GP3	5.2	5.81

Fig. 4. Flexural strength of geopolymer mortar after 7 and 28 days of curing.

Fig. 5. Geopolymer prisms while testing.

B. Impact Strength

After a curing period of 28 days, impact resistance test was conducted on 2 samples: a control sample and a sample including 2% RHF and 5% paper ash. The findings of the impact test are presented in Tables VIII and IX and Figures 6-8. The presented data indicate a positive correlation between the presence of fibers and the impact strength of the material. As fibers are added, the total number of strikes necessary for the sample to reach a state of crushing and failure exhibits a likewise increase. The enhanced ability to resist impact can be attributed to the interlocking of the fibers that are distributed randomly within the mortar, resulting in better energy absorption due to the incorporation of additional fibers. These results comply with the findings of [19, 20].

TABLE VIII. IMPACT TEST RESULTS AT 28 DAYS OF CURING

Sample	First crack-no of blows	Failure crack-no of blows
GPr	6	58
GP3	9	96

Fig. 6. Impact test results.

Fig. 7. Energy absorption results.

Fig. 8. Impact test.

V. COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS WORKS

Authors in [10] investigated the impact of including paper fibers on the characteristics of hardened normal concrete. After 90 days, the flexural strength demonstrated a substantial increase of 42.4%. Authors in [9] explored the impact of incorporating RHF similarly to this study at 1% of the mix volume of RPC. After 28 days of curing at 60 °C, the results showed that the compressive strength of the RPC samples increased by 7.4%. In this research, we designed a new geopolymer mortar with 30% metakaolin, 70% FA, RHF as reinforcement, and 5% waste paper ash as filler. The specimens were cured at 60 °C for 24 hr and then stored until the age of testing (7 and 28 days). The addition of 1%, 1.5%, and 2% of RHF and 5% of paper ash increased the geopolymer mortar flexural strength by 4%, 13%, and 25% at 7 days of curing and by 11%, 18%, and 31% at 28 days of curing. Although, only a 31% rise in flexural strength was achieved, it should be noted that most of the materials used in this research were sustainable and cost-effective compared to normal concrete.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a new geopolymer mortar with 30% metakaolin, 70% fly ash, rice husk fibers as reinforcement, and 5% waste paper ash as filler was designed and tested. The specimens were cured at 60 °C for 24 hr and then stored until the age of testing (7 and 28 days). Geopolymers are a suitable, environmentally friendly alternative to Ordinary Portland Cement for use in structural applications due to the utilization of sustainable and waste materials in its production. The following conclusions were achieved:

- The addition of 1%, 1.5%, and 2% of rice husk fibers and 5% of paper ash increased the flexural strength of the geopolymer mortar by 4%, 13%, and 25% at 7 days of curing and by 11%, 18%, and 31% at 28 days of curing.
- Impact tests showed that adding paper ash and rice husk fibers increased the impact and energy absorption by 50% for the first crack and by 66% for the sample failure after 28 days of curing.

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Analyzing the Influence of Microstructure on the Mechanical Properties of TIG Welded Joints processed by Friction Stir considering the sampling Orientation

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ABSTRACT

The contribution of the microstructural arrangement to the mechanical properties of friction stir processed Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welded joints is reported in this work. The TIG-welded joints were subjected to a single pass of Friction Stir Processing (FSP). The friction stir processed joint was sampled transversally and longitudinally, and different tests were conducted and studied comparatively. The microstructural analysis showed refined grains with varying degrees. The mean grain size for the transversally sampled specimen was found to be 11.48 μm , while the longitudinally sampled specimen had varying mean grain size from 7.32 μm to 15.09 μm . The varying mean grain size of the longitudinally sampled specimen is caused by the staggered arrangement of the microstructure. The tensile properties and the microhardness of the transversally sampled specimen were lower than those of the longitudinally sampled specimen. The ultimate tensile strength of the transversally sampled specimen was found to be 87.88 MPa which is lower than that of the longitudinally sampled specimen (133.83 MPa). The microhardness of the longitudinally sampled specimen fluctuated between 30 HV and 80 HV while the transversally sampled specimen had a maximum microhardness of approximately 57 HV.

Keywords-friction stir processing; sampling directions; microstructure; tensile strength; tungsten inert gas welding

I. INTRODUCTION

Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welding is a well-known joining technique best suited for soft metals like aluminum, copper, and magnesium [1, 2]. This technique operates on the principle of melting another metal with similar properties to the joined materials. The fact that there is high heat input involved in the procedure suggests that there are opportunities for the post-defects that can compromise the quality of the formed joint [3, 4]. This suggests that there is a need for the post-treatment required when one wants to enhance the quality of the produced or existing joint. There are many post-treatments that one can employ in enhancing the joint. This includes high-temperature and solid-state-based treatments like friction stir processing [5-7]. Friction Stir Processing (FSP) is a solid state-based microstructural modifying technique that uses friction to

generate the heat required to soften the material for microstructural modification [8]. FSP is a Friction Stir Welding (FSW) variant, but the distinction is that FSP requires or operates on a single surface, while FSW operates on more than one surface [9-12]. The FSP technique has been employed to modify the surface of metals by enforcing foreign particles and forming surface composites [13-16]. However, recent developments have shown that this technique can be employed in processing the joints produced using different techniques.

Authors in [17] have reported the influence of subjecting AA5083-H111 T-joints produced through gas metal arc welding to friction stir processing procedure. It should be noted that the FSP procedure was employed at the toe of the GMAW welds. The microstructural analysis revealed a clear grain variation from the weld to the processed area. The refinement of grains in the processed area resulted in improved hardness

and tensile properties compared to the weld. There was also a notable increase in fatigue life for the processed weld compared to the unprocessed weld. The unprocessed weld showed multi-nucleation site post fatigue test, whereas the processed joint showed significantly lower nucleation sites. The impact of applying FSP on the TIG welded joints was investigated in [18]. The normal procedure was used to produce TIG welded joints and later subjected to the FSP procedure. The microstructural analysis showed significant grain refinement at the nugget zone post-FSP procedure. This grain refinement contributed immensely towards enhancing tensile and microhardness properties compared to the TIG welded joint. However, it was observed that the mechanical properties of the base metal remained higher compared to friction stir processed TIG-welded joint and unprocessed TIG-welded joint. Authors in [19] analyzed the FSP procedure's influence on the AA6061/AA7075 TIG welded joints. The analysis conducted in this study included the prediction of heat transfer with the use of ANSYS software. The analysis also involved the variation of FSP parameters. It was discovered that the increase in rotational speed contributed to the refinement of grains and also impacted the heat input. This resulted in a reduction of residual stress while maximizing the tensile strength and hardness of the joint. It should be noted that all the samples tested in this study were sampled perpendicular to the welding direction.

The influence of FSP on the friction stir welded joints was investigated in [20]. The friction stir welded plates were subjected to the FSP procedure using the same welding setup. The microstructural analysis showed moderate grain refinement compared to the friction stir welded joint. A slight increase in mechanical properties was observed on the processed joints in comparison with the unprocessed ones. However, the mechanical properties of the joints were all less than those of the AA6082 base metal. All the analyses were performed on specimens sampled perpendicular to the welding direction. There are a few more studies where the FSP was employed on the joints [21-25]. However, it has been observed that most tests associated with joint analysis are performed on samples sampled perpendicular to the welding direction. This kind of analysis does not give full information about the actual joint. The information obtained in these analyses is mixed with the information outside the joint.

The current paper investigates the mechanical properties of the TIG welded joint when subjected to the FSP process. The main focus is on the analysis of the joint's behavior, considering the sampling direction, i.e. longitudinal and transversal. This kind of analysis could be useful to understand the strength of the joint and better configure components made from materials considered in this work.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

AA8011 and AA6082 plates were utilized, each 6 mm thick. These plates were initially prepared into rectangular shapes of 250 mm × 50 mm, with their end edges shaped into a V configuration of 60° in preparation for TIG welding. The welding process employed ER4043 filler material, the chemical composition of which was measured using Belec Spectroscopy [25] and is detailed in Table I. During welding, argon gas was

maintained at a flow rate of 28 L/min, the welding speed was set at 42 mm/min, and voltage and current were controlled at 37 V and 152 A, respectively. The FSP was conducted using the semi-automated LAGUN FA.1-LA milling machine [26]. FSP was executed with a tool rotational speed of 1100 rpm, a traverse speed of 55 mm/min, and a tilt angle of 2°. The tool used for the FSP procedure was produced from high-speed steel with a triangular-fluted pin profile, which was 5.8 mm long and with a diameter of 7 mm, as illustrated in Figure 1. Figure 2 illustrates a schematic diagram of the friction stir processed TIG-welded plate, with AA6082 positioned on the retreating side and AA8011 on the advancing side.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE WIRE FILLER [25]

Metal	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Cr	Ti	Zn	Al
ER4043	5.2	0.75	0.31	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.15	0.1	Bal

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the FSP tool.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the friction stir processed TIG-welded plate.

Waterjet technology was employed to prepare specimens for various tests, each test requiring both transverse and longitudinal sampling, as depicted in the schematic representation in Figure 3. Tensile testing was carried out using the Hounsfield 25K tensile machine, which was equipped with Horizon software. This specialized software is designed to directly extract tensile properties from the machine, eliminating the need for data postprocessing. The design and execution of the tensile tests adhered to the ASTM E8M-04 standard. Post tensile testing, the fractured surfaces were subject to analysis using scanning electron microscopy. Microhardness testing was performed using the InnovaTest Falcon 500 hardness testing machine, following the guidelines outlined in the ASTM E384-11 standard. All samples were subjected to a 300 g load with a dwell time of 10 s. To delve into the microstructural arrangement, the Motic AE2000 optical metallurgical microscopy was utilized, and grain visualization was achieved by applying two different etchants: a modified Keller's agent

for AA8011 which was found to be more effective and Weck's agent for AA6082. This combination ensured a clear and uniform grain structure throughout the entire stir zone without any over-etched regions [24]. Grain size measurements were conducted using ImageJ software, employing the linear intercept method, and subsequent calculations were carried out based on the acquired data. This grain measurement approach was adapted from the ASTM E112-12 standard [25].

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram depicting the sampling directions of different test samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the comparative analysis and discussion of the obtained results from the longitudinal and transverse directions.

A. Microstructure

Figure 4 illustrates the microstructural arrangement within the stir zone of the friction stir-processed TIG-welded joint. Specifically, Figure 4(a) provides a view of the stir zone sampled transversally, while Figure 4(b) depicts the longitudinally sampled specimen. To determine grain size in Figure 4(a), a recurring application of the linear intercept method was employed at various locations. The data collected from these measurements were then utilized to compute both the mean grain size and standard deviation, as detailed in Table II. Similarly, the mean grain size of the longitudinally sampled specimen was determined using a comparable methodology. However, due to its stacked configuration, the grain size measurements were taken from different vertical locations, leading to the presentation of L1-L3 data in Table II. Figure 5 offers insight into the microstructural grain distribution in relation to Figure 4. In the transversally sampled specimen, the mean grain size measured was 11.48 μm , with a standard deviation of 3.57 μm . In contrast, the longitudinally sampled specimen exhibited varying mean grain sizes within the range of 7.32 μm to 15.09 μm . This fluctuation in grain size indicates that different regions of the joint underwent dynamic recrystallization to varying degrees. It should be noted that the L3 region, which is closer to the surface in contact with the weld bed, displayed a defect-free nature and was dominated by exceptionally refined grains. This is attributed to the influence of the bed surface, where dynamic recrystallization and plastic flow are effectively controlled [27]. Furthermore, the longitudinally sampled specimen revealed the emergence of the strengthening precipitate, known as magnesium-iron, resulting from the interaction between AA8011 and AA6082 alloys [28].

Fig. 4. (a) FSP+TIG microstructural arrangement of the stir zone sampled (a) transversally, (b) longitudinally.

TABLE II. MEAN GRAIN SIZE AND STANDARD DEVIATION.

Joint	Mean grain size (μm)	Standard deviation (μm)
Transverse	11.48	3.57
Longitudinal L1	12.48	3.84
Longitudinal L2	15.09	6.74
Longitudinal L3	7.32	2.68

Fig. 5. Grain size distribution for (a) the transversally sampled specimen, (b) the longitudinally sampled specimen (i-iii).

B. Tensile Properties

The tensile specimens' post-tensile test results are shown in Figure 6(a), while Figure 6(b) shows the corresponding stress-strain graphs. The corresponding results are presented in Table III. The transversally sampled specimen failed at the center of the stir zone, while the longitudinally sampled specimen failed at the middle of the specimen. The transversally sampled specimen underwent a clear necking mechanism before fracture, while the longitudinally sampled specimen shows

unclear necking. The necking symbolizes that FSP did not bring enough microstructural defects healing at the center of the joint, thereby making this region the target for the failure initiation site. This failure also suggests that a nonuniform microstructural arrangement dominates the specimen. The stress-strain curves in Figure 6(b) clearly distinguish between the joint's tensile properties when subjected to transversal and longitudinal loads. The tensile strength of the specimen sampled longitudinally is higher than that of the transversally sampled specimen. The Ultimate Tensile Stress (UTS) values for the longitudinally and transversally sampled specimens are 133.83 MPa and 87.88 MPa, respectively. The tensile strain at UTS for longitudinally and transversally sampled specimens are 19.36% and 10.89%, respectively. The tensile strain values at the breakpoint for the longitudinally and transversally sampled specimens are 26.64% and 27.49%, respectively. The tensile properties of the longitudinally sampled specimen are higher than those of the transversally sampled specimen. This longitudinally sampled specimen's dominance in tensile properties is due to the fact that this specimen is dominated by refined grains observed during the microstructural analysis [29-31]. The refined grains contribute immensely to the tensile properties of the materials according to Hall-Patch relationship [32]. It is good to note that the longitudinally sampled specimens exhibit UTS that is way higher than AA8011 parent material and TIG welded joint but lower than AA6082 parent material. The UTS for transversally sampled specimens exhibits UTS that is lower than both parent materials but higher than the TIG welded joint [10, 33].

Fig. 6. (a) Fractured tensile specimens and (b) engineering stress-strain curves.

C. Fractography

Figures 7(a)-(b) show the fractography for the transversally and longitudinally sampled specimens, respectively. It should

be noted that the specimens fractured at the middle of the joint (transversally sampled specimen) and the specimen (longitudinally sampled specimen). Dimples of different sizes characterize the fractured surface of both specimens, which are ductile fracture characteristics. Numerous pores and voids are detected on the fractured surface of the transversally sampled specimen. These defects result from insufficient material flow and mixing, which contribute to the weakening of the joint. Dimples of different sizes dominate the longitudinally sampled specimen, suggesting ductile failure [10, 32-34].

TABLE III. TENSILE PROPERTIES

FSPed TIG	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile strain at UTS (%)	Tensile strain at breakpoint (%)	Position of fracture
Transverse	87.88	10.89	27.49	SZ
Longitudinal	133.83	19.36	26.64	Center

Fig. 7. Fractography for (a) transversally sampled specimen and (b) longitudinally sampled specimen.

D. Microhardness

Figure 8 depicts the microhardness profiles for transversally and longitudinally sampled specimens. The transversally sampled specimen shows a varying trend from the AA6082 base material toward the stir zone and a decreasing trend from the stir zone toward the AA8011 base material. This is a generic behavior for a joint composed of two dissimilar materials. The maximum microhardness at the stir zone for the transversally sampled specimen was 57 HV which is slightly higher than the TIG welded joint, followed by the sharp decrease toward the AA8011 side of the stir zone [10, 33, 36-38]. The sharp decrease may be caused by microstructural defects emerging from insufficient material mixing. The microhardness for the longitudinally sampled specimen shows a fluctuation across the thickness of the specimen, which is attributed to the variation in grain size observed during microstructural analysis. This is a manifestation of the joint composed of two dissimilar materials with unique mechanical

properties [39, 40]. The microhardness of the two specimens' configuration was found to be higher than that of the parent materials [33]. It was further observed that the microhardness profile involving dissimilar materials always follows an "S" shape unlike the "W" shape reported in the literature [41, 42].

Fig. 8. Microhardness profiles of the FSPed TIG weldments.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, the influence of microstructural arrangement on the mechanical properties of the friction stir processed TIG-welded joints with the main focus on the sampling direction was investigated. Based on the obtained results, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The microstructural arrangement of the joint varies with sampling directions. This was manifested during the measurement of the grain, where different locations of the longitudinally sampled specimen had different grain sizes. Another feature (strengthening precipitate) was also detected through the microstructural analysis of the longitudinally sampled specimen, which was not visible on a transversally sampled specimen.
- The tensile properties of the longitudinally sampled joint are way higher than those of the transversally sampled joint. This suggests that the joint responds differently to longitudinal and transversal loads.
- The fracture mechanisms for both longitudinal and transversal directions are similar, but the transversally sampled specimen showed some defects.
- The microhardness profile for both specimens is unique, and this uniqueness is due to the microstructural difference observed during microstructural analysis.

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Computation and Evaluation of the Electromagnetic Parameters of Amorphous Core Transformers

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an analytical model for computing and designing a three-phase Amorphous Core Transformer (ACT) with a power rating of 3 kVA, 380/127 V. Based on the main parameters obtained from the analytical model, a Finite Element Method (FEM) was developed to simulate the electromagnetic parameters, such as electric currents, operating voltages, and losses. Finally, an ACT installation was carried out with the steel material of code 2605SA1. The simulation results were compared with the experimental measurements under no-load and full-load operating conditions. Furthermore, the no-load loss of ACT was also compared to that of traditional transformers using silicon steel material. The obtained results prove that the use of ACT can save energy in the fields of education, health services, and industries.

Keywords-amorphous core transformer; current; no load; full load; finite element method

I. INTRODUCTION

The Amorphous Core Transformer (ACT) was first produced in the 1980s and was initially used as the steel core for electrical devices operating at high frequencies in the KHz range. However, later, it found applications as the steel core for industrial-frequency transformers. ACTs have special microstructural and compositional characteristics that reduce core losses: very low magnetic impedance ($H_C \approx 5-10$ A/m compared to $\sim 50-100$ A/m for silicon steel), thin thickness of steel laminations ($td \approx 0.03$ mm compared to $\sim 0.3-0.5$ mm for silicon steel), and very high resistivity ($\rho \approx 130-170$ $\mu\Omega$ cm compared to $\sim 50-60$ $\mu\Omega$ cm for silicon steel). These properties significantly reduce core losses in amorphous steel compared to best-quality silicon steel [1-2]. Currently, researchers and transformer manufacturers have constantly explored new materials, modified designs, and improved manufacturing technologies to enhance structure, shape, technical specifications economics, and reduce the no-load losses of transformers, such as eddy currents and hysteresis effects in the steel core [3]. The hysteresis loss depends on the material quality, while the eddy current loss depends on the thickness of the lamination stack. The no-load loss is a continuous loss throughout the operation of the transformer. As a result, the no-load loss constitutes a significant portion of the total losses in the transformer. Manufacturers are always looking for ways to

minimize transformer losses while also improving operational reliability [4]. Due to the unique core structure and rectangular winding of an ACT, the distribution of the electric field and the force acting on the winding will vary along the same coil. This distinction becomes more prominent during short-circuit events, which pose a significant danger to the winding [5]. The electromagnetic force exerted on the transformer winding arises from the interaction between the current and magnetic field in the windings. When the transformer operates under normal conditions, the influence of electromagnetic forces on the smaller winding is relatively minor due to the small magnetic field. However, during a short-circuit event, when the current in the winding and the magnetic flux increase significantly, a substantial electromagnetic force acts upon the winding. Among all transformer faults, winding-related issues account for 33% of the total, and these faults stem from short circuits: between turns of the High Voltage (HV) winding or Low Voltage (LV) winding, between different layers of winding, between HV and LV windings, and between phases in the same winding. These circumstances generate mechanical forces that can bend or damage the transformer winding [6-8].

In [5], the 2D Finite Element Method (FEM) was used to analyze and calculate the magnetic field of a 160 KVA ACT, considering the model in a short-circuit mode with maximum current. This study did not design an ACT model and did not

consider the 3D model under various operating conditions, such as no-load and rated load. In [9], the electromagnetic transients of a 25 KVA 3-phase oil-filled distribution transformer were analyzed using Ansys Maxwell simulation software. The simulation results provided values for losses, voltages, currents, and magnetic flux in the designed transformer, while the input voltage results aligned with the provided excitation values. Critical points on the core are discernible from the distribution of magnetic flux. The accuracy of the magnetic flux findings in this study was affirmed by comparison with similar studies. In [10], FEM was used to construct an analytical model for a 3-phase 50 MVA – 110/22 KV power transformer and to assess the impact of short-circuit impedance on the cumulative electromagnetic force effect. This study also involved subjecting the model to short-circuit current conditions to investigate the electromagnetic forces exerted on the transformer windings. In [11], a new model was developed to treat a 2D stress distribution problem, determining the stress distribution in the winding by solving the relevant equations. This study focused on the LV winding of a 110 KV transformer, which consisted of two continuously transposed conductors connected in parallel within a single disk, resulting in a model comprising two copper layers and one paper layer. Both the hoop stress and the radial stress distributions were calculated, and the obtained results were validated by FEM. Studies in [12-21] used FEM to analyze and compute the distribution of magnetic fields, impedance, and electromagnetic forces acting on the HV and LV windings of transformers during short-circuit operation. These studies provided formulas to calculate short-circuit currents and transient electromagnetic forces. In general, these studies provided results related to electrical losses, calculations, designs, and simulations focusing primarily on 22/0.4 KV distribution transformers. However, so far, there have been no specific studies on the design, experimentation, and simulation of lower-capacity ACTs with lower voltage levels.

This study used the analytic approach and FEM to calculate and design an ACT with small power capacity, commonly used as voltage stabilizers, power sources, or voltage converters in residential settings, educational institutions, small industries, industrial parks, and factories. The results obtained from the simulation were compared with measured results to validate the development of the proposed method. Based on the results obtained, it is possible to provide technical recommendations for the design, testing, and operation of ACTs.

II. ANALYTIC THEORY

A. Calculation of the Magnetic Circuit

The practical test was a 3-phase 3 KVA ACT, with primary and secondary voltages of 380/127 V, and a vector group of Y/Y_n . Figure 1 shows the structure of the ACT. The capacity power (S_i) for each core is defined as $S_i = S_{rated}/3$. This power depends on the material properties made of the iron core. Thus, the approximate formulation to define the cross-sectional area (T) of the iron core is [22-24]:

$$T = 2 \times c \times d = 4200 \text{ mm}^2 \quad (1)$$

where the magnetic flux density in the magnetic circuit is $B_i = 1$, and c and d are the thickness and depth of the steel core.

Fig. 1. Structure of ACT: $d=70$ mm, $c=30$ mm, $h=100$ mm, $w=50$ mm.

B. Computation of Windings

The turn numbers of the HV winding N_1 and LV winding N_2 are defined through the turn number winding per volt n_v as:

$$n_v = \frac{10^6}{4.44 \times B_t \times T \times f} = \frac{10^6}{4.44 \times 1 \times 4200 \times 50} = 1.1 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) gives $N_1 = 250$ turns and $N_2 = 83$ turns. By selecting the current density $J = 5 \text{ A/mm}^2$, the general winding diameter is calculated as:

$$d = 2 \sqrt{\frac{I}{\pi J}} \quad (3)$$

From (3), the diameter d_1 and the cross-section s_1 of the HV winding can be obtained as:

$$d_1 = 0.4 \sqrt{I_{1p}} = 0.4 \sqrt{4.56} = 0.9 \text{ mm}$$

$$s_1 = \left(\frac{d_1}{2}\right)^2 \cdot \pi = \left(\frac{0.9}{2}\right)^2 \cdot \pi = 0.5 \text{ mm}^2$$

Similarly, the diameter d_2 and the cross-section s_2 of the LV winding can be obtained as: $d_2 = 1.2 \text{ mm}$ and $s_2 = 1.1 \text{ mm}^2$. The layer number of electrical insulation m_1 of the HV winding is defined as:

$$m_1 = \frac{N_1}{n_1} = \frac{250}{100} = 2.5 \quad (4)$$

The width A_1 of the HV winding is defined as:

$$A_1 = m_1(d_1 + \gamma_1) = 3(0.9 + 2) = 8.4 \text{ mm} \quad (5)$$

where γ_1 is the thickness of the electrical insulation of the winding ($\gamma_1 = 2 \text{ mm}$), $m_1 = 3$ layers, and $A_1 = 10 \text{ mm}$ instead of $A_1 = 8.4 \text{ mm}$ given in (5). In the same way, the thickness of the LV winding A_2 is:

$$A_2 = m_2(d_2 + \gamma_2) = 2(1.2 + 2) = 6.4 \text{ mm} \quad (6)$$

where γ_2 is also the thickness of electrical insulation of the winding ($\gamma_2 = 2 \text{ mm}$), $m_2 = 3$ layers, and $A_2 = 8 \text{ mm}$ instead of $A_2 = 6.4 \text{ mm}$ given in (6). The width of the magnetic circuit window can be computed as:

$$\begin{aligned} w &= 2\delta_0 + 2\delta_{12} + \delta_3 + 2A_1 + 2A_2 \\ &= 2.2 + 2.1 + 5 + 2.10 + 2.8 = 47 \text{ mm} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

In general, the width of the magnetic circuit window is chosen bigger than 20-30% due to the winding layers being not flat [24]. Thus, $w = 50 \text{ mm}$. Finally, the cross-section area S_c is defined as:

$$S_c = h \times w = 100 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2 \quad (8)$$

Figure 2 shows all the design parameters. The basic electrical parameters and the design dimensions of the 3-phase 3 KVA-380/127 V ACT are also listed in Table I. Figure 3 illustrates the process of calculation, comparison, and development of the comprehensive simulation model from the initial design to the final results of this study.

Fig. 2. Cross-section structure of the ACT.

Fig. 3. Process of calculation of the ACT.

TABLE I. BASIC PARAMETERS OF THE ACT

No	Parameter	Value
1	Phase number	3
2	Frequency [Hz]	50
3	Rated power [kVA]	3
4	Wiring connection	Y/Y
5	Voltage of HV/LV [V]	380/127
6	No. of turns of HV/LV windings	250/83
7	Phase current of HV/LV windings [A]	4.56/13.64
8	Winding diameter d ₁ /d ₂ [V]	0.8/1.2
9	Electric current density J [A/mm ²]	5
10	Core thickness c [mm]	30
11	Width of core window w [mm]	50
12	Height of magnetic circuit window h [mm]	100

III. FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH

The ANSYS Maxwell tool (V19.R1) was used to calculate and simulate the electromagnetic parameters of the ACT [26]. Figure 4 shows the geometry of the 3 kVA-380/127V 3D-ACT. The problem was solved with different scenarios, including no-load, rated load, and short-circuit conditions.

Fig. 4. Amorphous Transformer in Ansys Maxwell 3D

A. No-Load Operation

Figure 5 illustrates the distribution of magnetic flux density in the magnetic circuit. It can be observed that most of the magnetic flux was concentrated in the magnetic circuit without in the air. The maximum value was 1.57 T. As a result, the leakage magnetic flux on the HV and LV windings was very small and nearly zero. Figures 6 and 7 show the waveforms of the HV and LV windings, respectively.

Fig. 5. Magnetic flux density distribution due to the 3-phase currents.

Fig. 6. Waveform of the HV winding.

In Figure 6, the simulation results indicate an effective phase voltage value of 218 V for the HV winding, compared to

the calculated phase voltage value of 220 V. Similarly, in Figure 7, the effective phase voltage value for LV was 72.4 V, compared to the calculated phase voltage of 73 V. For the no-load operation, the electric current in the LV winding was equal to zero. However, the no-load current in the HV winding was different from zero and is shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that the no-load phase current of the HV winding was 0.036 A. Figure 9 presents the joule losses for the no-load and full-load operations. The steady-state no-load loss value reached 10.5 W.

Fig. 7. Waveform of the LV winding.

Fig. 8. No-load current in the HV winding.

Fig. 9. Joule losses for no-load and full-load operations.

B. Full-Load Operation

Figures 10 and 11 show the distribution of the currents in the HV and LV windings, respectively.

Fig. 10. Rated currents in the HV winding.

Fig. 11. Rated currents in the LV winding.

Figure 10 shows that the simulated current in the HV winding was 4.53 A compared to the analytic current of 4.56 A. In the same way, Figure 11 shows that the value of the rated current in the LV winding was 13.51 A compared to the analytic current of 13.64 A. The rated loss reached 58.2 W.

IV. ACT MANUFACTURING AND ASSEMBLING

A. Manufacturing the Magnetic Circuit of ACT

A 3-phase 3 KVA 380/127 V ACT was assembled, as shown in Figures 12 and 13. The turn numbers of the HV and LV windings were $W_1 = 250$ and $W_2 = 83$ turns, respectively.

Fig. 12. Magnetic circuit assembling.

B. Diagram of No-Load and Rated-Load Experiments

Figure 14 shows the diagram of the no-load and rated load experiments [23-25]. First, the no-load operation was carried out to measure the values of no-load current, voltage, and joule loss.

Fig. 13. Completing the manufacture of ACT.

Fig. 14. Diagram of no-load and rated load experiments.

Then, the rated load experiment was carried out to measure the rated current and loss. Three 3kVA 380/127 V transformers were used to experimentally measure their no-load current and no-load loss: (1) SCT₁: Silicon core Transformer 1, (2) SCT₂: Silicon Core Transformer 2, and (3) the designed ACT. A comparison was carried out to determine the loss reduction capacity of the ACT design, as shown in Table II. From the results of Table II, it can be seen that the designed ACT had losses reduced by 75% compared to the SCT.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF NO-LOAD LOSS OF TRANSFORMERS

Parameter	SCT ₁ [25]	SCT ₂ [25]	Design ACT
No load loss P_0 (W)	48	42	11
No load current I_0 (A)	0.26	0.20	0.045
Rated current of HV winding $I_{rate-HV}$ (A)	4.6	4.6	4.56
Rate no load i_0 %	5.4%	4.1%	1%

C. Experimental Results

After carrying out the no-load and rated-load experiments, the results of currents, voltages, and joule losses were measured as given in Table III. It can be seen that the simulated values were smaller than the experimental values because the simulation did not take into account the characteristics of eddy currents, insulation materials, and the support structure of the transformers. Specifically, these errors fluctuated within the range of 2.2-5.9%. In particular, the error for the no-load current value was 25%. This substantial error arises because the no-load current value is very small and this error is influenced by the measurement equipment.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF THE SIMULATED AND MEASURED RESULTS

No	Parameter	Simulated results	Measured results	Errors (%)
1	No load current I_0 (A)	0.036	0.045	25
2	$I_{rate-HV}$ (A) of HV winding	4.53	4.80	5.9
3	$I_{rate-LV}$ (A) of LV winding	13.51	14.2	5.1
4	U_{1HV} (V) of HV winding	218	225	3.2
5	U_{1LV} (V) of LV winding	72.4	74	2.2
6	No load loss P_0 (W)	10.5	11.0	4.7
7	Full load loss P_r (W)	58.2	61.5	5.6

V. CONCLUSION

This study involved the calculation, design, and production of a 3-phase 3 KVA 380/127V ACT. In addition to the analytical method, FEM and an experimental method were carried out under both no-load and rated-load conditions. The simulated results for the rated voltage, current, and no-load and rated-load losses were compared and evaluated against the experimental data. The error assessment displayed an oscillation range of 2.2-5.9%, indicating that the accuracy between the two methods is nearly equivalent. This study also successfully designed and manufactured a 3-phase 3 KVA, 380/127V ACT to experimentally prove the ability to reduce the no-load losses of this design. This study opens up new possibilities to design and manufacture energy-efficient transformers, not only for high power but also for smaller capacities and lower voltage levels. These results can serve as experimental models and educational tools for universities and research institutions.

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Finite Element Analysis of a Double Beam connected with Elastic Springs

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ABSTRACT

This paper develops a finite element method for double beams subjected to static loading. The double beam consists of two Euler–Bernoulli beams connected continuously by an elastic spring connection. The finite element for a double beam is formulated with eight degrees of freedom based on the Euler–Bernoulli beam theory. The finite element method is implemented in MATLAB software to analyze the behavior of the double beams. The MATLAB code calculates the displacements of both the upper and lower beams. Numerical examples are compared with the analytical solution to demonstrate the high accuracy of the proposed method.

Keywords-double beam; FEM; elastic springs

I. INTRODUCTION

Common structural forms in civil engineering and mechanical, such as beams [1-5], frames [6, 7], plate and shell structures [8-15], have garnered significant attention from the researchers. Problems related to beams and frames are significant in various engineering fields such as mechanical and civil engineering, for example, in the design of bridges, and railway systems. The beams rest on a foundation subjected to static or dynamic loads have been extensively studied for many years with various models foundations, including the Winkler foundation model [16], the two-parameter Pasternak foundation model [17], and the viscoelastic foundation model [1]. Authors in [18] improved the two-parameter foundation model based on the theory of Winkler-Zimmerman and Vlasov-Leontyev to calculate the internal forces of the beam resting on the elastic foundation with two parameters using the finite element method.

In engineering, there are structures composed of two layers of materials bonded together with a thin adhesive layer or some

simple connections. These structures can be approximated and analyzed as composite beams with resilient or nonlinear connections. For example, a composite beam model can be applied to approximate the behavior of sandwich beams [3, 19]. Authors in [20] investigated accurate solutions for the dynamic problem using the improved Wittrick-Williams algorithm and the stiffness matrix method. The dynamic stiffness method and the Wittrick-Williams algorithm to calculate the dynamics of a double-beam system with a viscoelastic layer were employed in [21]. The stress and strains in the multilayered beam are solved analytically in [22] in which the assumption of the interaction of layers is nonideal. Authors in [23] used an analytical method with the state function to solve the oscillation problem of a double beam system with a viscoelastic intermediate layer. Authors in [24] calculated the oscillations of a double beam with concentrated masses using an analytical approach. Authors in [25] obtained analytical solutions for the dynamics of a double Euler-Bernoulli beam system subjected to moving loads using trigonometric series. The dynamic response of a double-beam subjected to moving force was investigated using analytical methods [26] considering various symmetric

boundary conditions. The buckling analysis of composite rods made of three timber layers with consideration for the nonlinear shear deformation of the timber layers is researched in [27] using a semi-analytical method. There have been numerous studies on the behavior of double beams, but most focus on dynamic analysis using analytical methods. This paper performs finite element analysis for double beams with an elastic layer under static loading conditions. The computed results of the proposed approach are compared with those obtained from the analytical solutions.

II. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION FOR DOUBLE-BEAMS

Let us consider a double beam consisting of two beams connected through an elastic layer with stiffness k_w , as shown in Figure 1. The double beam element is shown in Figure 2. The displacement fields are approximated by interpolation functions as follows:

$$\begin{cases} w_{Upper}(x) = N_1 u_1 + N_2 u_2 + N_3 u_3 + N_4 u_4 \\ w_{Lower}(x) = N_1 u_5 + N_6 u_6 + N_3 u_7 + N_4 u_8 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$[K]_e = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{12EI_1}{L^3} & \frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & -\frac{12EI_1}{L^3} & \frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & \frac{4EI_1}{L} & -\frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & \frac{2EI_1}{L} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{12EI_1}{L^3} & -\frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & \frac{12EI_1}{L^3} & -\frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & \frac{2EI_1}{L} & -\frac{6EI_1}{L^2} & \frac{4EI_1}{L} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{12EI_2}{L^3} & \frac{6EI_2}{L^2} & -\frac{12EI_2}{L^3} & \frac{6EI_2}{L^2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{6EI_2}{L^2} & \frac{4EI_2}{L} & -\frac{6EI_2}{L^2} & \frac{2EI_2}{L} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{12EI_2}{L^3} & -\frac{6EI_2}{L^2} & \frac{12EI_2}{L^3} & -\frac{6EI_2}{L^2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{6EI_2}{L^2} & \frac{2EI_2}{L} & -\frac{6EI_2}{L^2} & \frac{4EI_2}{L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1. Double beam.

The potential energy of an elastic layer of element is:

$$U_w = \int_0^L \frac{1}{2} k_w (w_1 - w_2)^2 dx = \int_0^L \frac{1}{2} k_w ([N]\{U\}_1 - [N]\{U\}_2)^2 dx \quad (7)$$

The stiffness matrix of an elastic layer is:

The interpolation functions are defined as:

$$\begin{cases} N_3 = 3\frac{x^2}{L^2} - 2\frac{x^3}{L^3} & N_1 = 1 - 3\frac{x^2}{L^2} + 2\frac{x^3}{L^3} \\ N_4 = x\left(-\frac{x}{L} + \frac{x^2}{L^2}\right) & N_2 = x\left(1 - 2\frac{x}{L} + \frac{x^2}{L^2}\right) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The displacement vector of finite element:

$$\{q\}_e = \{u_1 \ u_2 \ u_3 \ u_4 \ u_5 \ u_6 \ u_7 \ u_8\}^T \quad (3)$$

The stiffness matrix for the upper and bottom beam:

$$[K]_e^1 = \int_{V_{e1}} [B]^T [D][B] dV_1 = E \int_{A_1} y^2 dA \int_0^L [N']^T [N''] dx \quad (4)$$

$$[K]_e^2 = \int_{V_{e2}} [B]^T [D][B] dV_2 = E \int_{A_2} y^2 dA \int_0^L [N'']^T [N'''] dx \quad (5)$$

The stiffness matrix of the element is shown in (6):

$$K_w = k_w \int_0^L \begin{Bmatrix} [N] \\ -[N] \end{Bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} [N] & -[N] \end{Bmatrix} dx \quad (8)$$

Fig. 2. Double beam element.

$$[K]_w = k_w \begin{bmatrix} \frac{13L}{35} & \frac{11L^2}{210} & \frac{9L}{70} & \frac{13L^2}{420} & \frac{13L}{35} & \frac{11L^2}{210} & \frac{9L}{70} & \frac{13L^2}{420} \\ & \frac{L^3}{105} & \frac{13L^2}{420} & \frac{L^3}{140} & \frac{11L^2}{210} & \frac{L^3}{105} & \frac{13L^2}{420} & \frac{L^3}{140} \\ & & \frac{13L}{35} & \frac{11L^2}{210} & \frac{9L}{70} & \frac{13L^2}{420} & \frac{13L}{35} & \frac{11L^2}{210} \\ & & & \frac{L^3}{105} & \frac{13L^2}{420} & \frac{L^3}{140} & \frac{11L^2}{210} & \frac{L^3}{105} \\ & & & & \frac{13L}{35} & \frac{11L^2}{210} & \frac{9L}{70} & \frac{13L^2}{420} \\ & & & & & \frac{L^3}{105} & \frac{13L^2}{420} & \frac{L^3}{140} \\ & & & & & & \frac{13L}{35} & \frac{11L^2}{210} \\ & & & & & & & \frac{L^3}{105} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Sym

Fig. 3. Loads on double beam element.

The force vectors on the element for distributed loads on the upper beam are:

$$\{P\}_e = \int_0^L \begin{bmatrix} 1 - 3\frac{x^2}{L^2} + 2\frac{x^3}{L^3} \\ x - 2\frac{x^2}{L} + \frac{x^3}{L^2} \\ 3\frac{x^2}{L^2} - 2\frac{x^3}{L^3} \\ -\frac{x^2}{L} + \frac{x^3}{L^2} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} p_0 dx = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p_0 L}{2} \\ \frac{p_0 L^2}{12} \\ \frac{p_0 L}{2} \\ -\frac{p_0 L^2}{12} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

III. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

A. Example 1

The first example was conducted to verify the results of the finite element method presented above with the analytical solution [28]. In this section, the simply supported double beam is composed using two rectangular cross-section beams connected through an elastic spring with a length of 10 m, subjected to a uniformly distributed load of $q = 10$ kN/m.

Fig. 4. Simply supported double beam.

Comparing the results obtained from the finite element method and the analytical method, the difference is usually very small, indicating good agreement between the two approaches.

TABLE I. DISPLACEMENTS AT THE MIDDLE BEAM

Stiffness k (N/m)	Upper beam			Bottom beam		
	Present (FEM)	Analytic solution [28]	Error (%)	Present (FEM)	Analytic solution [28]	Error (%)
1E+05	33.375	33.375	0	8.2917	8.2918	1.2E-3
1E+06	23.5322	23.522	0	18.1446	18.1447	5.5E-4

Figure 5 shows the shear force and bending moment diagrams for the upper and bottom beam. The upper beam subjected to a direct load lead to significant bending moment, while the bottom beam is smaller bending moment. Conversely, the shear forces between the upper and bottom beams show minimal difference.

Figure 6 illustrates the displacements of the upper and bottom beams with varying stiffness of the elastic springs. The results show that as the stiffness increases, the difference in displacement between the two beams decreases gradually. The results show that the interaction between the two beams depends significantly on the stiffness of the elastic layer. As the stiffness of the elastic layer increases, more load is transmitted from the upper to the lower beam, resulting in a decrease in the displacement of the upper beam and an increase in the displacement of the lower beam. When the stiffness of the elastic layer becomes very high, the displacements of both beams become equal.

Fig. 5. Double beam: Free upper and bottom beams. (a) Shear forces, (b) moment.

Fig. 6. Displacement of beam and stiffness of the elastic layer.

B. Example 2

The double beam is composed using two rectangular cross-section beams connected through an elastic spring with a length of 10 m, subjected to a concentrated load $P = 10$ kN, as shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Double beam: Free upper beam and bottom beam.

Fig. 8. Double beam: Free upper and bottom beams. (a) Shear forces, (b) moment.

Figure 8 illustrates the moment and shear force diagrams of the double beam with a concentrated force at the middle upper beam. In this case, the shear force distribution between the upper and lower beams differs due to the placement of the force at the midpoint of the upper beam. The moment in the upper beam at the midpoint is significantly greater than that in the bottom beam.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The paper successfully developed a finite element formulation for the double beam with a viscoelastic intermediate layer using classical beam theory. The displacements of the upper and lower beams were approximated using the Hermitian cubic interpolation functions to construct the beam stiffness matrix. The computed results were compared with the analytical solutions, demonstrating the reliability of the analytical approach in this study. The analysis of the beam displacements with different values of the layer stiffness parameter revealed a significant influence of this layer on the displacements of both the upper and lower beams in the double beam system.

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Rotor Bearing Casing with added Polymer Particle Composite

Analysis of Acoustic Emission Measured Results

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ABSTRACT

The trend of production machines with higher operation speeds brought the issues of vibration amplitude and acoustic emissions to the surface. To solve this problem, a standard approach requiring mass and/or stiffness increase, and utilizing high-damping polymer composite materials, e.g. by adding them to the empty spaces of the original structures is employed. The presented polymer composite application is for rotor bearing casing in which the polymer particle composite is added into the mechanical system by filling the empty space between the rotor bearing casing and the housing body. Before this application, an analysis of four polymer composite samples with different compositions was made. Then the logarithmic decrements were measured by two experimental methods and one composite was selected. The application showed acoustic emission maximum amplitude reduction of 67% and 33% when excitation amplitudes are low (up to 5 g) and large (above 10 g), respectively. In the case of the FFT spectrum of acoustic emissions, the reduction was 85% and 51%.

Keywords-particle composite; damped component; logarithmic decrement; time record; FFT spectrum

I. INTRODUCTION

When increasing the production machines working speed, a state in which resonance occurs can be reached. The most effective way to reduce the vibration amplitude is to increase the mechanical system damping. One way to achieve this is by using material damping. The damping parameters are very low for a standard structural material such as steel. Cast iron and aluminum can be classified as standard structural materials, which have better material damping than steel, but the desired damping effect is not so significant. So, non-standard construction materials and their structures come into consideration. The usual sources of Acoustic Emission (AE) are material failure in the form of fracture (brittle, tough, etc.), plastic deformation, decohesion, inclusions, corrosion, leakage of the operating medium, flow of the operating medium, and the surrounding environment (wind, noise, vibrations). So, AE can be used in fracture mechanics, to determine either the material mechanical state or the presence of corrosion. It is advantageously used for continuous monitoring of complex structures condition in aviation, construction industry, geological engineering, energy production, etc. In production

technologies, it can be used to determine tool wear during cutting to check the technological procedure steps. At the same time, AE analysis along with vibration analysis are well-known methods of testing and monitoring the condition, especially of bearings fault diagnosis [1-3], geared shafts and gears [4, 5], oil viscosity [6], production processes [7-9], manufacturing processes [10-12], etc. AE can detect very low energy loss processes due to friction or cavitation. These loss processes create waves of energy in the macrostructure and microstructure due to dislocation and degradation procedures. In the mentioned fields, the AE (noise) is an unwanted effect, however in [13], the sound waves generated by developed acoustic cyclone separator are used for acoustic air cleaning equipment.

Polymers are materials with good damping, but their stiffness and strength are not satisfactory for common engineering applications. However, composites with a polymer matrix find applications in mechanical engineering in the fields of machinery and technology production. Composites of particle-shaped reinforcement (also called polymer-concretes) are the most often ones used in the mentioned fields. Fiber-

reinforced polymer composites are also utilized in machinery, mainly due to their high stiffness and strength. They have satisfactory material damping, but it is not as significant as the damping of polymer -particle composites. High damping materials, e.g. lead rubber bearings, are applicable as seismic protection means, even in nuclear power plants. The non-isolated response is 2-3 times larger than the response of base-isolated structures [14]. The industrial bearings of machines and their faults are important vibration sources and AE for which monitoring and evaluation techniques are developed [15].

Each production machine represents a mechanical system consisting of components that naturally have their own mechanical compliance, which is one of the sources of vibration and subsequent AE. When measuring the response in the form of vibrations or AE, it is the response of the entire system, which is being measured rather than that of its individual members. Thus, the excitation point (input) and the output point in the form of a working member (tool) are important in a mechanical system. However, individual components located in the mechanical system between the input and the output as well as their connections or placement in the fluid can either increase or decrease vibrations and AE. To increase damping in mechanical systems with steel components while the contact stiffness is maximum, high material damping can be inserted into the mechanical system. Of course, the weight and stiffness of that system are also increased, but these values are negligible compared to the weight and stiffness of other components. These high-damping materials manifest themselves most significantly in the area of resonant working speeds.

II. DETAILS OF EXPERIMENT

A. Materials and Procedures

Before the rotor bearing casing application, we made four samples for testing, the detailed description of which is in Table I. The fillers A-D of samples S1-S4 differ mainly in the size of silica sand grains and their composition expressed by volume ratio.

TABLE I. SAMPLES

	S1	S2	S3	S4
Matrix:filler (Volume ratio)	1:3.5	1:3	1:3	1:2
Epoxy resin: Fixative (volume ratio)	100:50	100:16	100:16	100:50
Size of individual fillers (mm)	Filler A: 0.1-0.3	Filler A: 0.1-0.3	Filler A: 0.1-0.3	Filler D: 0.1-0.8
	Filler B: 0.3-1 Filler C: 2-4	Filler B: 0.3-1	Filler C: 2-4	
Volume ratio of fillers	2:3:5	1:1	1:1	1
Average size of fillers (mm)	1.735	0.425	1.600	0.45

The following measuring devices and software were used: Acoustic emission sensor Vallen-VS45-H with a range of 20 kHz–400 kHz, Dynamic Signal Acquisition device NI-9223 module meter, signal level ± 10 V, resolution 16 bit, sample rate 1 MS/s/ch, software for advanced analysis of the dynamic

signal base on LabView Sound and Vibration Toolkit, National Instruments Corporation.

B. Application Description

The rotor bearing driven by a flat belt is a source of vibration for the housing unit (Figure 1), which is part of the textile machine mechanical system. The reduced vibrations, which are the sum of the housing unit reduced vibrations, the bearing in the casing, and vibrations in the bearing individual parts, manifest in reduced AE. The native design of the rotor casing is shown in Figure 2. That design involves a casing and tube in which the rotor is mounted when operating. The native design was designed for a lower rotational speed than the increased rotational speed at which it is expected to operate.

Fig. 1. Housing unit, its parts, and acoustic emission sensor.

Fig. 2. Rotor casing (a) photo, (b) drawing.

Therefore, the native design stiffness is insufficient when the speed is increased to 100,000-130,000 rpm, and the increased deformations contribute to the amplitudes augmentation. The indicated speeds are in the first half of the resonance peak. Several designs of rotor casing were realized, namely those with a reinforced tube and different types of rubber filling at each side of the casing. This article presents the modification of the design by using an additional polymer particle composite (Figure 3), which contributed to increasing material damping in addition to increasing stiffness and mass. Stiffness, weight, and damping are three usual quantities affecting the dynamic behavior of mechanical systems. Dynamic behavior is visible in the form of the time record of vibrations when exciting, which from a theoretical point of view can be considered harmonic.

Fig. 3. Rotor casing with polymer particle composite (a) photo, (b) drawing.

The rotor bearing is inserted inside the rotor casing with polymer particle composite (Figure 4). Both components are mounted in the housing unit (Figure 1). The rotor is driven by a belt in contact with a pin that is part of a rotor.

Fig. 4. Tested rotor casing with a rotor bearing inside.

C. Determination of Logarithmic Decrement

If we compare viscous and hysteresis damping models for a case of a mechanical system with a single degree of freedom and free vibration decaying effect, the model selection practically has no effect [16]. This applies in practice to conventional models with a damping ratio $\zeta < 0.2$. The measurement instruments for the determination of the logarithmic decrement were: Polytec PDV 100 contactless vibrometer and LabView software. Plots of time and frequency domain response were evaluated by hand calculation according to (7) and (8).

1) Decrement Determination from the Time Domain Curve

The measurement is based on the transient response of a Single Degree Of Freedom (SDOF) mechanical system on the impulse excitation force, i.e. the free vibration response [17, 18]. The tested material sample represents the SDOF mass-damper-spring vibration system whose dynamic behavior of mass m depends on spring and damper constants k and c , respectively. The equation of underdamped motion ($\zeta < 1$) for free damped vibrations of an SDOF mechanical system is:

$$x(t) = X_0 e^{-\zeta\omega_n t} \sin(\omega_d t + \phi) \quad (1)$$

where x is the underdamped displacement (amplitude, distance from equilibrium) of the mass for free vibrations effect of mechanical system, X_0 is the amplitude, ζ is the damping ratio,

ω_n and ω_d represent the undamped and damped natural frequency, respectively, and ϕ is the phase angle.

Fig. 5. Polymer particle composite, sample S1: (a) time domain response curve of 0.2 s, (b) frequency domain curve.

The logarithmic decrement δ , expressing the rate of decay, is defined by:

$$\delta = \ln \frac{x_1}{x_2} \quad (2)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the amplitudes of two successive cycles (Figure 5(a)). According to (1), for displacements x_1 and x_2 , it can be written:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1(t_1) &= X_0 e^{-\zeta\omega_n t_1} \sin(\omega_d t_1 + \phi) \\ x_2(t_2) &= X_0 e^{-\zeta\omega_n (t_1 + T_d)} \sin(\omega_d (t_1 + T_d) + \phi) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $t_2 = t_1 + T_d$ and T_d is the damping period.

Substituting (3) to (2) and using $T_d \omega_d = 2\pi$, we obtain:

$$\delta = \zeta\omega_n T_d = \zeta\omega_n \frac{2\pi}{\omega_d} \quad (4)$$

The relation between undamped and damped natural frequencies is:

$$\omega_d = \omega_n \sqrt{1 - \zeta^2} \quad (5)$$

Substituting (5) to (4) and arranging, we obtain the relation for damping ratio ζ :

$$\zeta = \frac{\delta}{\sqrt{4\pi^2 + \delta^2}} \quad (6)$$

2) *Decrement from the Frequency Domain Curve*

To be able to use a method based on the frequency domain, we need the frequency response function. In general, a Fourier transformation converts a signal of the time domain to the frequency domain, i.e. we obtain the frequency domain response spectrum. In our case, the Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) is used through the NI Labview software. This method of damping ratio evaluation is named the half-power bandwidth method or the 3 dB method. The values at the resonant peak (Figure 5(b)), determine the damping ratio ζ as follows:

$$\zeta = \frac{\omega_2 - \omega_1}{2\omega_n} \tag{7}$$

where ω_1 and ω_2 are frequencies corresponding to the half-power point, i.e. a $1/\sqrt{2}$ drop from the resonant peak value. On a decibel scale, this would correspond to a 3 dB drop from the peak [19].

In the case of light damping, it is suitable to use the simplified formula $\delta \approx 2 \pi \zeta$ resulting from (6).

III. RESULTS

The measured results of logarithmic decrement determined by the method of free-damped vibrations and the half-power bandwidth method are listed in Table II. Based on the measurement and availability of polymer- particle composite components, we created for application the polymer particle composite according to sample S4. To determine the logarithmic decrement, (2) was adjusted to evaluate the set of vibration cycles:

$$\delta = \frac{1}{n} \ln \frac{x_i}{x_{i+1}} \tag{8}$$

where n is number of cycles and x_i is the i -th amplitude of the i -th cycle.

TABLE II. LOGARITHMIC DECTEMENT Δ

Sample	δ Method of free damped vibrations	δ Half-power bandwidth method	Arithmetic mean	Δ (%)
S1	0.8493	0.7555	0.8024	-11.04
S2	1.0790	0.9195	0.9993	-14.78
S3	1.0352	0.7923	0.9138	-23.46
S4	1.0486	0.8828	0.9657	-15.81

A comparison of the existing and new designs was made at a steady excitation rotational speed of 135,000 rpm, which is the area of resonance. AE results were evaluated in the range of 50 to 400 kHz. Two modes of excitation by rotor generating amplitudes were tested: to 5 g and above 10 g, corresponding to excitation by suitable and unsuitable rotors.

Figures 6(a)-(b) show the time records of the AE amplitude response of the native design (black) and the new design (green), respectively.

Fig. 6. Time records of AE of native (black) and new design (green): (a) excitation up to 5 g, (b) excitation above 10 g.

Fig. 7. FFT spectrums of AE of native (black) and new design (green): (a) excitation up to 5 g, (b) excitation above 10 g.

The FFT spectrums in Figure 7 show significant reduction mainly for excitation up to 5 g, where the amplitude reduction is about 85%. The FFT spectrum of the new design (green) shows new frequency peaks. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III. SUMMARY OF RESULTS

		Excitation amplitude up to 5 g		Excitation amplitude above 10 g	
		native	damped	native	damped
Additional mass (grams)		-	70	-	70
Mass (grams)		92	162	92	162
Time record	Maximum amplitude (V)	0.012	0.004	0.036	0.024
	Maximum amplitude reduction	-	66.6%	-	33.3%
	Amplitude reduction efficiency E_a (-)	-	0.876	-	0.438
FFT spectrum	Maximum amplitude (V PtP)	0.00151	0.00023	0.0092	0.0045
	Maximum amplitude reduction (V PtP)	-	84.7%	-	51.1%
	Frequency peaks (kHz)	100, 160, 190	100, 160, 190	50, 100, 165, 190	15, 30, 100, 155, 190
	Amplitude reduction efficiency E_a (-)	-	1.114	-	0.671

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The current paper presents an application of polymerparticle composite in the rotor bearing casing. Before application, analysis of four polymerparticle composite samples with different compositions was conducted, the logarithmic decrements were measured by two experimental methods, and one composition was selected for the considered application. The presented application is for rotor bearing casing in which the polymer- particle composite is inserted into the mechanical system by filling in the free space between the casing and the housing body. The application showed beneficial results for other similar applications in production machines. The study outcomes are summarized as:

- For the time domain, the reduction of acoustic emission maximum amplitudes was 67% and 33% when excitation amplitudes were up to 5 g and above 10 g, respectively.
- For the FFT spectrum of acoustic emission, the reduction was 85% and 51%.

The novelty of the presented application lies in operation with extreme rotational speeds in the resonant area. The polymer particulate composite is filled in a relatively small cavity of the joint, resulting in the ability to increase the operational speed with minimum time of design modification and costs. The mentioned features make the presented approach very effective. The results are consistent with the results of

applications based on adding high-damping capacity materials such as aluminum foam sandwiches and carbon fiber-reinforced polymers [20], particulate reinforced polymer composites [21], and particulate damper [22] into machine tool structures.

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Solar Water Heating Systems: A Review on Contemporary Design and Emergent Technology using PCM for Increased Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study highlighted the specificity of solar water heating systems, investigating their financial benefits and discussing their economic advantages. Several studies have shown that solar water heaters' effective performance and the best cost savings were obtained during the hot seasons. New developments in solar water heaters have been discussed in detail. According to numerous researches, the highest quality performance of solar water heaters and the best cost savings were achieved when the system was integrated with innovative components such as Phase Change Materials (PCMs), heat pipes, and turbulators. Emergent technologies using PCMs have shown excellent results, increasing solar thermal efficiency. This technology presents great potential not only for domestic applications but also on an industrial scale.

Keywords-solar water system; emergent technology; collector; PCM; performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The building sector around the world is projected to consume up to 100 quadrillion BTU of energy in 2035 [1]. In many countries, population growth and rapid economic development have led to a rise in energy consumption that accelerates the depletion of local resources and increases greenhouse gas emissions [2]. Renewable energy sources are exploited to generate electricity. Solar thermal energy is a technology to harness solar energy and convert it into thermal and/or electrical energy. In 2016, the installed thermal heat capacity globally reached 456 GWh [3]. Although the contribution of thermal solar heating is underestimated in many countries, this contribution is the second largest energy production after wind energy and is more important than the photovoltaic solar energy production. Solar thermal energy production competes with conventional renewable energies such as hydroelectricity and biomass [4]. Heating water with fossil fuels requires significant energy consumption and poses economic and environmental problems. Solar Water Heater Systems (SWHSs) are a modern alternative energy source to provide hot water, replacing and limiting fossil fuels consumption. SWHSs need increased public awareness of their benefits to enlarge their adoption and are classified among the environmentally friendly contributions of renewable energy [5].

Solar water heaters can be categorized into two main types: active and passive. Both systems harness the energy of the sun to heat water but differ in their operational mechanisms, efficiencies, and applications [6-7]. They are essentially based on solar radiation or the heat of heat transfer fluids from a collector to heat water [8]. Solar water heaters can eliminate 50 tons of carbon dioxide emissions in 20 years [9]. A conventional SWHS consists of a panel with solar collectors and an insulated tank with a size large enough to store hot water and maintain the desired heat. There are different types of solar water heaters, such as integrated storage solar water heaters, flat plate thermosiphonic units, and evacuated tube thermosiphonic units. The integrated storage SWHS is made up of solar collectors and water storage tanks in one unit [10]. These systems are simple in terms of manufacture and less expensive than other systems while being able to produce hot water up to 200 l/day [11-12]. The disadvantage of integrated solar water heaters is the increase in thermal losses during the night due to the water tank [13-14]. These heat losses are still poorly understood despite several encouraging results [15-16]. Indeed, several studies have investigated the improvement of the thermal performance of SWHSs to reduce these losses [17-19]. In addition, many studies have investigated technologies to develop energy-efficient and high-performance solar power systems [20]. These systems can be used in different types of engineering applications depending on the production mode, such as cooling and heating systems in buildings [21-22],

SWHSs [9, 23], solar air heating [24-25], solar storage tanks [26], photovoltaic thermal systems [27-28], solar thermal power plants [29-30], refrigeration and air conditioning [31-32], solar stills [33-34], textile industry [35], and smart electronic devices [36-37].

This study illustrates the world trend to use renewable energy, particularly solar energy, encouraging the development of technological solutions for water heating. It also highlights the performance of SWHSs, analyzes their financial benefits, and compares their economic advantages with other water heating systems. In addition, the efficiency of different collector materials is investigated, along with a comprehensive review and description of the performance of various solar collector designs as well as the challenges associated with the installation of SWHS.

II. RENEWABLE ENERGY POLICIES AND INITIATIVES AROUND THE WORLD.

Worldwide, many governments have introduced and implemented energy management systems and policies related to energy efficiency and renewable energy schemes. Table I shows the main initiatives. Based on these strategies, the development of SWHS was encouraged through different research programs and grants.

TABLE I. RENEWABLE ENERGY POLICIES AND INITIATIVES AROUND THE WORLD [38]

Country	Renewable energy policies and initiatives
Australia	The government decided to create and maintain a regulated and competitive energy market for the propagation of energy harnessing using cost-effective, efficient, and clean technologies
Brazil	Focus on biofuel-based projects owing to the presence of the Amazon Rain Forest on its mainland
China	Takes the issue of climate change seriously and has put in place several policies regarding the conservation of ecology and environment for sustainable development and better socio-economic future of the country
EU	20% reduction in the emission of greenhouse gases, 20% increase in overall energy efficiency, increased contribution of renewable energy by 20%, increased contribution of biofuels for transport by 10%.
USA	Does not have an effective policy regarding renewable energy systems

III. CONTEMPORARY PERFORMANCES

SWHSs have many advantages, such as financial benefits, energy performance, and efficiency.

TABLE II. MONTHLY ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF CENTRALIZED SWHS AND CONVENTIONAL UNITARY ELECTRIC HEATERS IN HONG KONG [42]

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Electricity consumption of unitary electric heaters (GJ)	207	175	185	174	170	160	162	162	162	180	185	205
Electricity consumption of centralized solar water-heating (GJ)	125	80	95	110	93	75	65	65	70	75	70	103

According to [42-44], the lack of information on the lifespan of solar water heaters and the low cost of electric resistance water heaters do not encourage consumers in Brazil to use SWHS. In [45], it was reported that it is more

A. Financial Benefits

To study the feasibility of SWHSs, an economic evaluation is essential to improve consumer awareness of their benefits. In [39], the cost of SWHS and its financial benefits were studied in a residential area in Pakistan. The replacement of water heating using electricity by SWHS made it possible to save €430.95, while the replacement of water heating using natural gas with SWHS saved €67.81 in energy costs per household per year. The cost of installing solar water heaters is high but can be recovered after a period of use. The payback period for SWHS installation varies from 1.16 to 1.38 years for electricity; however, the payback period for natural gas water heaters is longer and varies between 6.95 and 8.27 years. According to [40], replacing electric water heating with SWHS saves 4163.98 kWh of electrical energy per year. An SWHS reduces CO₂ emissions by 2206.9 kg, SO₂ by 2.08 kg, and NO₃ by 75 kg per year. Materials and installation costs for solar water heaters have been estimated at \$337,000. Replacement of electric water heaters saves 1146 GJ. With the cost of one kWh corresponding to \$0.12, the annual savings on electricity costs would be \$37,606.30, and the repayment period would be 9.2 years. Due to the local economic recession and deflation over the past few years, net worth has not been taken into account. Thus, the discount factor cannot be determined as a result of economic growth. Furthermore, the estimated cost of electric water heaters is \$85,665.87. Based on these financial studies, the first net cost of a SWHS would be 249,858.80 USD. With savings in electricity, the repayment period for installation and material costs would be only 6.9 years and can be further shortened. The thermal transmission of solar water heaters varies depending on the architectural design and the orientation of the collectors. Right positioning and orientation make it possible to have a considerable part of the solar radiation, which would be converted by the SWHS to heat water. In [41], it was shown that using PV/T collectors with west orientation can reduce heat gain by more than 50% in summer. For domestic applications, electricity consumption depends on the mode and frequency of electrical appliances use. The main obstacle to an SWHS installation is the high cost of installation and heating system equipment. To encourage the installation of SWHS, governments need to introduce economic incentives and benefits to users. As a result, installation and hardware costs will be more affordable and attractive to consumers. Table II presents the monthly electricity consumption of centralized SWHSs and conventional unitary electric radiators. These measurements show that the electricity consumption of electric heaters is higher than that of SWHSs. Furthermore, consumption is very high in December, January, February, and March.

economically profitable for public services to finance large-scale SWHS projects for low-income populations. The results show that given the high costs, the low-income population does not have the means to install and buy SWHSs. In addition,

SWHSs have several advantages for consumers, such as financial savings in electricity costs and energy savings. Solar water heating is more feasible if the payback period for installation and material costs is shorter [46]. The diffusion of SWHS in different areas is due to national and regional subsidy programs, tied to government programs. Furthermore, the size of SWHSs is related to the volume of hot water used daily by consumers. The surface of the solar radiation collectors and the hot water storage are calculated according to the hot water consumption of each consumer and the climate of each period and place.

B. Energy Performance

In [5, 35], high-rise centralized SWHSs were evaluated, and in [40], thermal solar collector networks were installed at great heights to support hot water consumption. According to meteorological data, the annual average efficiency of solar collectors could reach 38.4%. Thus, the solar fraction reaches 53.4% with an installation cost recovery period of 9.2 years. With the increase in electrical energy consumption expenses, the return on investment would be even shorter than the classic

payback period. Table III illustrates the monthly thermal gain of the solar collector arrays on the south and west façades. The simulation results of the thermal model show that from the southern network, thermal gain can be obtained during the cold season (September - March). On the other hand, from the western network, the thermal gain is higher during the hot season (April - August). This variation trend agrees with the incident solar radiation on the façades of the solar collectors. In addition, the use of two solar panels gives an important performance throughout the year (except January and April) and a relatively stable thermal energy production. Furthermore, the annual thermal gains of SWHSs are different depending on the location of installation. The thermal gains are higher in the south than in the west, corresponding to 478 GJ in the south and 426 GJ in the west. Therefore, a total solar radiation collector surface of 840 m² can produce 904 GJ per year. Consequently, overall performance is 1.08 GJ/m² per year. On the other hand, based on solar radiation measurements, the incident solar radiation on the south facade is 1216 GJ, and on the west façade it is 1141 GJ.

TABLE III. MONTHLY THERMAL GAIN OF ARRAYS OF SOLAR COLLECTORS TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT SOUTH AND WEST FAÇADES OF BUILDINGS [48]

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Thermal gain in south (GJ)	40	48	41	22	25	26	27	34	42	57	65	55
Thermal gain in west (GJ)	19	29	34	29	41	54	59	50	40	32	23	19
Total	59	77	75	51	66	80	86	84	82	89	88	74

C. Efficiency

Table IV presents the average efficiency of collectors according to their base materials [49]. The results show that copper and aluminum solar collectors have the lowest efficiency of 56 and 59%, respectively. Black- and blue-coated copper solar collectors have higher efficiency than aluminum collectors, with 63 and 60%, respectively. On the other hand, vacuum-tube solar collectors have the highest yield with an efficiency of 75%. Solar collector usage is linked to the payback period.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE EFFICIENCIES FOR DIFFERENT COLLECTOR MATERIALS [47]

	Black coating selective Cu	Blue coating selective Cu	Cu solar collector	Aluminum solar collectors	Vacuum tube collector
Efficiency %	63	60	56	59	75

Despite the low competence of copper or aluminum solar collectors, these types of SWHS are the most widely used in the world, mainly due to their lower cost, which is a key factor in convincing the user to install an SWHS [5]. The SWHS application size plays an important role without involving the selection of the right solar collectors. Large-scale applications, such as industries, large housing estates, and public swimming pools, require a big number of plates and solar collectors to cover the need for hot water. These applications require large areas and cost too much to install [9]. Despite their high installation and material cost, high-efficiency solar collectors for heavy use are the best choice, as they provide high energy savings and shorter payback periods. Unlike large-scale applications, residential applications require a low unit cost

with high hot water efficiency. Therefore, the cost of collector installation and maintenance, the equipment cost, and their efficiency are important factors in the choice of SWHSs. Based on these reports, the cost and efficiency of SWHSs with aluminum collectors and vacuum tubes are the best choices for the production of thermal energy and heating water.

D. Different Material Specifications

The base material of the solar collectors has a strong influence on the efficiency and appeal of SWHSs. The systems used are copper, aluminum, copper with selective blue or black coating, and vacuum tube collectors. Table V shows the material specifications for the manifolds. Each material has its specifications [47]. As the black selectively coated copper collector has the highest length and width of 187.5×88 mm, this header material has the highest gross surface area. In addition, each collector has a different absorber material. For a copper with black selective coating collector, the absorber material is a selective copper coating. For a blue selective coated copper collector, the absorber material is a selectively coated copper tube. For copper or aluminum headers, the absorber materials are special black-painted copper and black-painted aluminum pipes, respectively. In addition, the collector's front cover varies depending on the SWHS and the collector material. The front cover of copper collectors with black selective coating is made of tempered solar glass. On the other hand, the other collectors (aluminum, copper, and copper with blue coating) are tempered regularly. From a cost point of view, the most expensive material is the copper manifold with black selective coating and the vacuum tube manifolds which are equal to \$704.63, and the least expensive is the aluminum one which is equal to \$422.78.

TABLE V. MATERIAL SPECIFICATIONS FOR THE MANIFOLDS IN THE COLLECTORS AND EFFICIENCY OF SWHS [49]

	Black coating selective copper thermosiphon	Blue coating selective copper collectors	Copper solar collector	Aluminum solar collectors	Vacuum tube collector
Dimensions (mm)	187.5×88	185.5×86	186×86	187.5×87.5	-
Gross area (m ²)	1.65	1.6	1.6	1.65	1.6168 (for 20 tubes)
Absorber	Selective coating copper	Copper tubes with selective coating	Special copper collectors painted black	Black-painted aluminum pipes	Cu/AL/SS/N ₂
Front cover	Tempered solar glass	Regular tempered	Regular tempered	Regular tempered	-
Price (\$)	704.63	598.94	528.47	422.78	704.63

E. Technical Specifications

Although SWHSs with lower standard efficiency solar panels are widely used, there is still significant power-saving potential in the utilization of more efficient panels [7, 48]. The use of more efficient solar collectors shows potential savings of 65-71% for split systems and 83-91% for thermosiphon systems. The performance of SWHSs may vary in the solar panel orientation as opposed to the north; for example, the east and west orientation of the collector can result in up to 80% reduction in electricity saving. South- and center-oriented collectors result in not only a significant drop in energy efficiency but also a critical level of protection from Legionella. Performance is also greatly affected by the tilt angle of the solar panel. For example, mounting collectors vertically on a building façade reduces the solar fraction and Legionella, depending on latitude. Standard dust accumulation levels in solar panel glass are reduced by 5% compared to clean solar panels, resulting in a 20-24% increase in SWHS power consumption. Under extreme dust accumulation, for example, a 64% reduction in transmission, the annual power consumption of the SWHS increases by a factor of 5-6.

IV. TYPES OF SOLAR COLLECTORS

A very important aspect in improving the energy efficiency of a SWHS lies in the formulation of collector design features: the type and size of the CPC reflector, combined with materials with improved optical properties, and the low iron glass or double glass application for the transparent cover of the absorbing surface [20]. In [49], a storage solar collector with storage tanks was presented, where the accumulator was made of six copper tubes with an outer diameter of 80 mm, the pipes were painted with regular black matte paint, the copper pipes were connected in series with an outer diameter of 15 mm, and a thin layer of paraffin was placed under the absorber to keep the heat from the sun. During sunny hours, liquid paraffin acts as a heat source and transfers heat to the absorber. Rigid styrofoam panels were used to insulate the system. The results demonstrated that the system could keep the collector plate temperature above 40°C for more than 4 hours after the sun's rays dropped in the afternoon.

Some studies used Phase Change Materials (PCMs) in solar collectors, which can be categorized into three main types: organic, inorganic, and eutectic. Each of these types has its own set of advantages, limitations, and potential applications [50]. In [51], a PCM-integrated flat plate collector was designed and manufactured. Nine risers were attached to the top surface of the absorber plate while 37 fins were attached to its bottom surface. PCM was added to the underside of the absorber plate. The riser-absorber fin configuration acts as a

heat exchange unit, swapping thermal energy between the PCM and the water, while the fins increase the heat transfer area between the PCM and the absorber plate. In this study, two PCM types were used: (i) paraffin and (ii) paraffin nanocomposites containing 1.0 wt% of 20 nm nanocopper particles. Three case studies, without PCM, with PCM, and with Cu-PCM nanocomposites, were conducted at 10°, 20° and 30° tilt angles. At the end of the 24-hour run, the system without PCM had a tank temperature of 35.1°C at 7:00 am. On the other hand, the tank temperatures of the PCM and Cu-PCM nanocomposite systems were 40.1 and 40.7°C, respectively. For each material, the efficiency of SWHS was variable with a best angle of inclination equal to 10°. The efficiency was around 52.0% for the system with the Cu-PCM nanocomposite, 51.1% for the system with PCM, and 47.6% for the system without PCM. The thermal conductivity of the nanocomposite is 24% higher than that of pure paraffin wax. With the addition of paraffin wax collectors, collector competence increased by 6.9%. On the other hand, the addition of CuPCM nanocomposite improved efficiency by 8.4%.

In [52], a household SWHS with solar panels coupled with a phase-change energy storage device was proposed. The system consists of a water tank, solar collectors, pipes, and a data acquisition system. The solar panel was 1800 mm long. The PCM memory was installed in the collection tube. The diameter, wall thickness, and length of the PCM memory cells were 42.16, 1.53, and 1.720 mm, respectively. In this study, Ba(OH)₂·8H₂O was used as PCM, while a small amount of BaCO₃ was used as a nucleating agent. U-shaped copper tubes were embedded in the PCM as heat transfer tubes. The results highlighted that the heat output of the system was lower than that of conventional water-in-glass vacuum-tube solar water heaters with the same collection area. However, if the system is run at a constant flow rate, excess energy can be stored and released to reheat the water when the sun's rays fade. As a result, the system exhibited better performance than conventional systems.

Reducing the proportion of diffuse global radiation or the initial water temperature improves solar water heaters performance. In [53], a new method was proposed to integrate dual PCMs into solar vacuum tube collectors for SWHS. The double PCMs used in the study were tridecane (melting point 72°C) and erythritol (melting point 118°C). The results showed that the PCM integrated into the inner tube of the vacuum tube solar collector can effectively store latent heat due to the thermal insulation of the vacuum tube. Therefore, when the sun is not strong enough, it delays supplying heat to the system. The outcomes revealed that the proposed SWHS with PCM integrated into the vacuum solar tube collector had an

efficiency improvement of 26% and 66% in normal operation and stagnation mode, respectively, compared to the standard SWHS without PCM. When using an SWHS consisting of a vacuum Heat Pipe Solar Collector (HPSC) and an LHS tank filled with PCM, solar energy is absorbed by the heat pipe evaporator section and transferred to the Heat Pipe Condenser (HPC) section. Heat is stored in the LHS tank. The stored heat is then transferred to the water supply and heated through a series of finned tubes located within the LHS tank. The results showed that the thermal efficiency of the system was 38-42% and 34-36% on sunny and rainy days, respectively. Furthermore, when increasing the water flow from 50 to 80 l/h, the overall system effectiveness improved in the test area. The results also showed that the system had no thermal stratification effects. Table VI shows the performance of some recent solar collector designs.

TABLE VI. PERFORMANCE OF SOME RECENTLY DEVELOPED SOLAR COLLECTORS

Ref.	Performance of developed solar collectors
[49]	After the sun goes down in the afternoon, keep the collector temperature above 40°C for 4 hours.
[51]	Keep the water temperature above 50°C for 1 hour.
[52]	Continue to increase the temperature of the water tank for 2 hours after the sunlight decreases in the afternoon
[53]	Keep the water temperature above 40 °C for more than 2 hours, without PCM

It should be noted that some intrinsic parameters related to PCM materials, such as the thickness and coating uniformity, can affect solar collectors performance [54-46]. In [57], PCM with a coating layer thickness of 160.1 μm in the MA/NBR-0.5 pellet recorded the highest latent heat of melting and freezing compared to other coated samples, due to the formation of a thin and compact coating layer. Table VII summarizes some solar collectors integrated with PCMS with different system configurations.

TABLE VII. RECENT STUDIES ON SOLAR COLLECTORS INTEGRATED WITH PCMS

Ref	System Configurations	Findings
[54]	Use of stearic acid ($K = 0.32\text{-}0.34 \text{ W/m}$) as a PCM	Maximum daily energy outputs of collector A were found to be 85.86% (simultaneous mode) and 84.27% (midday charging mode) at a high mass flow rate (0.5 LPM), and energy outputs were 19.41% and 21.35%, respectively, at a low flow rate
[55]	Combined utilization of phase-change materials and fins in addition to nanoscale fluids to enhance electrical efficiency.	When using PCMs, the thermal, electrical, and overall efficiency improved by 26.87%, 17.33%, and 40.59%, respectively
[56]	The PCM used in the study was Beeswax (INS No. 901) or yellow beeswax (CAS No. 8006-40-4)	The average efficiency of the CTC-GT test mode at a collector angle of 25°, 30°, and 35° was 30.7%, 31.9%, and 31.7%, while CTC-GT mode provided 27%, 29.9%, and 29.6%.
[58]	Heat Pipe ETC (HPETC) integrated with PCM embedded with porous copper	The system showed 85.64% energy efficiency compared to a system without PCM which showed 36.91% energy efficiency.

V. OPPORTUNITIES

The performance of a building-integrated SWHS is more dependent on the quality of the system design rather than the individual SWHS products. Solar collector effectiveness is only one part of the system's performance, and the thermal energy storage and transfer to end users are also critical to the final performance. Additionally, due to the unreliability of solar energy, many SWHS building integration projects opt for a further energy supply system, usually that of electricity or natural gas. More systems come into play when the solar thermal system fails at night or under adverse weather conditions. However, in practice, the two systems not only increase users initial installation cost but also pose a major challenge to the system design. Simultaneously a poor system design can lead to more energy waste and higher energy bills. For example, repeatedly boiling a large amount of water in a tank to maintain its operating temperature when a solar system is not in operation for a long time can consume a lot of electricity or gas.

VI. CHALLENGES

Solar water heaters use solar energy to heat water or heat pumps that use air heat. Water heating can be expensive and energy-intensive. Compared to electric hot water systems, solar water heaters can help households save significantly on electricity bills and reduce emissions by up to 3 tons per year. Solar water heaters adoption peaked in 2009 when the federal government introduced discounts to make the technology more attractive ahead of plans to phase out electric hot water systems [38]. Since then, the market share of SWHSs has continued to decline, with sales in 2016 decreasing by 15% from the previous year. This decline was seen in all states and territories except Tasmania, where sales increased slightly. The Northern Territory saw the greatest drop, with sales decreasing by almost 40%.

VII. CONCLUSION

This article provides a comprehensive investigation of recent innovations in solar water heaters, emphasizing their enhanced performance and cost-efficiency when incorporating advanced components such as PCMs. Despite the high installation and material expenses, solar water heaters save the cost of electricity if their use is long-term. Considering technology, vacuum tube solar collectors have the highest effectiveness, followed by black- and blue-coated solar collectors. Aluminum collectors come in the fourth place. Storage tanks competence was also examined, and it was obviously higher when the PCMs were encapsulated in spherical capsules or cylindrical containers. The addition of PCMs results in smaller water storage tanks that are capable of retaining hot water for a longer period. Encapsulated PCMs can be easily added to existing storage tanks. However, the performance of an integrated SWHS in a building is more dependent on the quality of the system design than the individual SWHS products. Emergent technologies such as artificial intelligence-based optimization to reduce health risks and improve long-term performance. These technologies aimed to achieve the technical feasibility of SWHS with PCM and

may be future opportunities that can be used to develop mathematical models to simulate and optimize design options.

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Design, Modeling, and Control of a Brushless Permanent Magnet Motor for Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Electric Vehicles (EVs) are becoming more and more common. In addition to their ecological advantages, EVs have demonstrated their efficiency in curtailing travel expenses by transitioning from gasoline to electricity, which is significantly less costly. This study proposes a Brushless Permanent Magnet Motor (BPMM) design for EVs, models the influence of average and ripple torque, and evaluates its efficiency compared to other designs. The validity of the proposed design was supported by simulation results.

Keywords-*brushless permanent magnet motor; electric vehicle (EV); control analysis; EV design; PI controller*

I. INTRODUCTION

The problems of vehicle environmental effects and fuel consumption are getting worse as a result of the vastly expanded number of vehicles on the road. The urgent call for cars with high fuel efficiency and minimal emissions attracts significant interest from all corners of the society. Many alternative drive trains, including fuel-cell hybrid vehicles, have been proposed to address this problem [1-2]. To improve overall efficiency, the motor is either used to supplement or replace the conventional internal combustion engine. The battery provides power to the all-electric car whereas its main issue is the reasonable-sized battery limited driving range. In a hybrid electric vehicle, the battery and internal combustion engine function as a single hybrid energy source. Under two or more sources, control becomes more complex while the driving range and system efficiency increase. However, hybrid electric cars cannot fully achieve zero emissions while the internal combustion engine is present [3-4].

The growing cost of fossil fuels and their carbon emissions have been the main drivers of the mandate for renewable energy adoption. Solar and wind power are among the most popular renewable energy resources among energy suppliers and researchers [5-6]. PV and wind sources, on the other hand, are unpredictable in their operation. The power produced by PV and wind is highly dependent on solar irradiation and wind speed [7-8]. As a result, effective storage devices are used to ensure a constant power supply. Fuel cell benefits include an efficient and extraordinary power density and a flexible

structure. Electric applications greatly favor the proton exchange membrane fuel cell due to its small size, high power density, and low noise emission [7-8]. Fuel cells are the best alternative for reliable power because of their low environmental impact. Their slow thermodynamic and electrochemical properties allow them to respond to transient conditions as quickly as needed [9-11]. Performance can be adjusted by controlling the interfacing devices that connect them to the electrical grid. Additionally, a single cell's voltage output is insufficient for grid connection. Many fuel cells are linked in both parallel and series configurations to provide a large DC voltage [12-14]. Unfortunately, the system cost grows and the fuel cell competence declines as the number of fuel cells expands. High-gain converters [15-17] are used to overcome this problem, transforming low voltage into high. Boost converters are characterized by their high gain and low-duty ratio. In contrast, high-duty ratio operation improves converters' otherwise poor efficiency [18-19].

To obtain a high gain in a low-duty cycle, a converter was presented in [20-21] using a linked inductor and a high-frequency grade transformer. Converters were expensive and needed consistent maintenance. Several different maximum power point tracking techniques were thoroughly discussed in [22-25]. A better optimization strategy was established in [26-28] to improve the energy extraction from fuel cell implementations. An enhanced dynamic cuckoo search algorithm was developed for practice in fuel cell solicitations, dealing with the drawbacks of the conventional approach,

which did not adjust the duty cycle depending on varying environmental temperatures. In [29-31], a new PV/fuel cell setup was designed to optimize the system linked to the grid, evaluated in three different grid load scenarios.

This study focuses on the modeling, analysis, and design approach for permanent magnetic synchronous motors used in EVs. The proposed interleaved design of the permanent magnet alternating current motor was validated in MATLAB/Simulink. The interleaved inverter ensures minimization of output current ripples as well as the system reliability.

II. MODELING THE BPMM FOR EV

SS equations are used to calculate motor voltage and current:

$$V_{qs}^r = r_s I_{qs}^r + w_r L_d I_{ds}^r + w_r \lambda_m' \tag{1}$$

$$V_{ds}^r = r_s I_{ds}^r - w_r L_q I_{qs}^r \tag{2}$$

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} \frac{p}{2} [\lambda_m I_{qs}^r + (L_d - L_q) I_{qs}^r I_{ds}^r] \tag{3}$$

The step input goes through a low-pass filter to control disturbances in the V_{dc} output. This low-pass filter is arbitrarily chosen. The step input goes through a current regulator block (4), which is a voltage-based current modulator:

$$v_{qs}^r = w_r L_d i_{ds}^r + w_r \lambda_m + k_q (i_{qs}^r - i_{qs}) \tag{4}$$

A. Current Regulator

A current regulator is an electrical circuit or device that controls the current flow in a circuit even when the supply voltage or load resistance vary. In other words, it guarantees that the current flowing through a circuit stays constant even when other elements such as the load's resistance or power supply voltage vary. The charging and discharging of an electric vehicle's battery are regulated by a control system called the battery current regulator. The battery current regulator's job is to make sure that whether the battery is being charged or discharged, the current flows within safe working parameters.

A PI controller block can be used to create the battery current regulator in Simulink, as shown in Figure 1. The Battery Management System (BMS) provides the PI controller with the difference between the required current and the measured current as input. The battery's charging and draining are then managed using the PI controller's output. The output signal is calculated by the PI controller using a Proportional (P) and Integral (I) gain. The integral gain offers a delayed reaction to minimize any steady-state faults in the output signal, whereas the proportional gain offers a direct response to the difference between the intended and measured currents.

An essential part of an EV's electrical system is the battery current regulator, which certifies that the battery is charged and discharged safely and effectively. The battery current regulator controls the current flow to the battery, preventing overcharging and overheating, which can cause damage or even battery failure. From (4) we can get:

$$I_{qs}^r = \frac{K_d - I_{qs}^r}{r_s + L_q} \tag{5}$$

Fig. 1. PI current regulator block diagram.

B. Pulse Width Modulation (PWM)

An EV uses a current modulator, which is an electrical component to regulate the amount of current flowing from the battery to the motor. It is necessary to the powertrain system and is in charge of the vehicle's smooth functioning. Figure 2 shows the modulator block (sine triangle PWM with third harmonic injection). The intended stator voltages, the rotor position, and the DC voltage are the inputs of the modulator block. For transistors, the outputs serve as switching signals.

Fig. 2. Block diagram for the pulse width modulation modulator.

If the voltage increases over 1, the premise regarding PWM is nullified. Signal strengths are within ± 1.5 and are separated by 120° . An electronic device, known as a motor controller, controls the speed, torque, and direction of an electric motor. Such devices are typically used to control the movement of machines and equipment in various industries, such as manufacturing, robotics, and automation. Motor control works by adjusting the power supplied to the motor. It receives signals from the control system or the operator telling the amount and direction of current to supply to the motor. The controller then adjusts the power delivered to the motor accordingly using techniques such as Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) and Direct Current (DC) control.

III. DESIGN OF A BRUSHLESS PERMANENT MAGNET MOTOR (BPMM)

ENSTROJ produces the high-performance EMRAX 208 electric motor, which can be employed in both aerospace and electric car uses. It is a Brushless Permanent Magnet Motor (BPMM) with a liquid cooling system that can run on both AC and DC power sources to provide dependable performance in challenging tasks. The motor is perfect for weight-sensitive uses, such as electric aircrafts, because it is lightweight and has a high power-to-weight ratio. This type of motor is highly productive, with a stated efficiency of over 95% in high-power settings.

The number of poles in a motor is an important parameter that affects its speed-torque and other performance characteristics. In general, a higher number of poles in a motor leads to a lower speed and higher torque output, while a lower number of poles leads to a higher speed and lower torque output.

$$p\lambda_{qs}^r = v_{qs}^r - r_s i_{qs}^r - w\lambda_{ds}^r \quad (6)$$

$$p\lambda_{ds}^r = v_{ds}^r - r_s i_{ds}^r - w\lambda_{qs}^r \quad (7)$$

$$\lambda_{ds}^r = L_d i_{ds}^r + \lambda_m \quad (8)$$

$$\lambda_{qs}^r = L_q i_{qs}^r \quad (9)$$

$$T_e = \frac{3P}{2} [\lambda_m i_{qs}^r + (L_d - L_q) i_{ds}^r i_{qs}^r] \quad (10)$$

The flux constant of the BPMM, also known as the back-EMF constant, depends on the specific version or variant of the motor. The standard version of the motor has a flux constant of approximately 0.0275 V/(rad/s), or equivalently, 0.00438 V/(rpm). This means that for a given rotor speed in radians per second (rad/s), the back-EMF generated by the motor is approximately 0.0275 times the speed in volts. Similarly, for a given rotor speed in revolutions per minute (rpm), the back-EMF is approximately 0.00438 times the speed in volts.

The flux constant is an important parameter that describes the relationship between the motor's electrical and mechanical characteristics. Specifically, it relates the back-EMF generated by the motor to its rotational speed and can be used to determine the motor's torque output and efficiency under different operating conditions. The standard version of the motor has a rated stator resistance of approximately 0.046 Ω at 25°C. However, this value may vary depending on the specific motor and operating conditions. The stator resistance is an important parameter that affects the motor's performance and efficiency. It determines the amount of power loss due to the resistance of the stator windings and can affect the current, torque, and speed characteristics of the motor. It is typically measured and specified at a reference temperature, such as 25°C, and may change as the motor heats up during operation.

The inductances of the BPMM on the d -axis and q -axis depend on the specific version or variant of the motor. The d - and q -axes inductances are important parameters that affect the motor's performance and control characteristics. They determine the rate of change of the magnetic field in the motor's rotor and can influence the motor's torque and speed characteristics under different operating conditions. The inductances are typically measured and specified using standard test methods, such as the three-phase short-circuit method or the two-phase open-circuit method.

IV. SIMULATION OF THE PERMANENT MAGNET MOTOR (BPMM)

Simulink is engaged to calculate and plot the maximum torque-versus-speed envelope and maximum mechanical power-versus-speed for a given drive system. The simulation was performed using MATLAB code. The code considers various parameters, such as the number of poles, flux constant, stator resistance, inductances, battery voltage, filter parameters,

and current and voltage limits. The optimal BPMM was applied to the EV model to create a Simulink-based simulation model that combined the forward and backward simulation models. In another way, the driving schedule requires a certain torque and speed from the vehicle, and each module needs the required torque and speed from its superior module in the direction of the backward simulation data flow. When the data flow reaches the final energy storage, the battery will provide the required amount of energy. The simulation results are plotted, showing the maximum torque versus mechanical speed and the maximum mechanical power versus mechanical speed, as shown in the following figures.

Fig. 3. Maximum torque of the BPMM.

Figure 3 illustrates the maximum torque versus mechanical speed for a specific system. Up to 700 rad/s, torque is limited by current, but beyond that, both current and voltage constraints come into play. A step change in I_{qs}^r was simulated while keeping the mechanical speed constant. The simulation plots the stator voltages, stator currents, DC voltage output, DC current, battery current, and electrical torque over time. Figure 4 depicts the system's response to the step change in I_{qs}^r , displaying the variation of DC voltage output (V_{dc}) over time from the filter block. Although it is expected to be 350 V, it fluctuates between 348V and 352V due to high-frequency harmonics in the inverter current (I_{dc}). Figure 5 shows the stator a -phase voltage (V_{as}) as a function of time. The peak value corresponds to approximately 2/3 of V_{dc} , which is around 233 V, as expected. The voltage values change in five distinct steps (2/3, 1/3, 0, -1/3, -2/3) of V_{dc} at the starting time. Since the BPMM acts as an EV's traction machine, performance analysis across the speed range is required. Figure 6 demonstrates the torque envelopes. The ideal machine produces more torque in the high-speed range and less torque in the low-speed range compared to the original BPMM.

Fig. 4. Build up the DC voltage of the BPMM.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of the stator a-phase voltage (V_{as}) of the BPMM.

Fig. 6. Electric torque (T_e) of the BPMM.

When a step change occurs, it takes approximately 3 times the time constant ($\tau = Kq / (rs + Lq)$) for T_e to reach a steady-state value of around 100 Nm. The maximum value is approximately 210 A, but the current exhibits significant noise and fluctuates rapidly between the maximum value and zero. Figure 7 illustrates the battery current (I_{bat}) as a function of time. During positive I_{qs}^r , the maximum value is approximately 91 A, which closely matches the calculated value. When I_{qs}^r changes to negative, there is an immediate recharging cycle.

Fig. 7. Control of the battery current in the EV.

Fig. 8. Control of the battery current in the EV.

Fig. 9. Harmonic spectrum of the optimal BPMM.

Figure 8 shows the stator a-phase current (I_{as}) as a function of time. It exhibits a sinusoidal waveform with a peak amplitude of 208 A, slightly below the input value of 210 A. At 0.05 s, there is a phase shift of 180° due to a negative step. The no-load-back EMF of the ideal BPMM at a base speed of 1200 rpm is sinusoidal. The pertinent harmonic spectrum is computed in the interim. Figure 9 illustrates that the total harmonic distortion (THD) is merely 2.8%.

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a BPMM design, modeled, and controlled to meet the demands of various driving situations for EVs. It was shown that the proposed design approach considered the maximum operating torque and performance requirements to respond to the demands of various driving scenarios for EVs. The proposed design approach, which considers the maximum operating speed and performance requirements throughout the entire torque range, was shown to work well to produce a preliminary BPMM with good performance. The viability of using a BPMM in an EV was demonstrated by both analysis and simulation results, validating its optimization results for EV traction devices.

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Forecasting Tariff Rates and Enhancing Power Quality in Microgrids: The Synergistic Role of LSTM and UPQC

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ABSTRACT

The current paper presents an original approach into the microgrid control framework by incorporating LSTM-based optimization with specific emphasis on refining the gain parameters of a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller. This integration represents a significant advancement in improving the overall efficiency of microgrid control systems. By creatively applying LSTM optimization, the paper achieves dynamic adjustments of the PID controller's parameters, resulting in more precise regulation of output power quality. Through the utilization of the Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC) in conjunction with LSTM-based optimization, the paper establishes a compelling link between improved power quality and the resultant tariff rates. This highlights their combined influence on enhancing power quality and calibrating tariff rates, providing a fresh perspective on optimizing microgrid operations.

Keywords formatting; microgrid; forecasting; LSTM; UPQC; power quality

I. INTRODUCTION

In an era characterized by increasing energy demands, growing awareness of environmental sustainability, and a desire for energy resilience, the concept of microgrids has emerged as a transformative solution for our evolving energy landscape. Microgrids represent a paradigm shift in the way we generate, distribute, and consume electrical energy [1-2]. Unlike traditional centralized power grids, which rely on large power plants and long-distance transmission lines, microgrids are localized, self-contained energy systems that serve specific communities, campuses, industrial facilities, or even individual buildings. The fundamental idea behind a microgrid is to decentralize and democratize energy generation and management. These self-sufficient energy ecosystems integrate a diverse mix of energy sources, including solar panels, wind

turbines, Combined Heat and Power (CHP) systems, and energy storage technologies. Through advanced control systems and digital technologies, microgrids can intelligently balance supply and demand, optimize energy use, and seamlessly transition between grid-connected and islanded (standalone) modes [3-6].

The development of precise forecasting technologies is essential for successfully tackling the supply-demand complexities in contemporary energy management. These forecasts are segmented into specific time frames, to meet the precise energy management requirements of the microgrids. In the ultra-short term, which encompasses periods ranging from a few seconds to half an hour, the primary emphasis is placed on dynamic control for renewable power generators and load monitoring [7-8]. Real-time adjustments are employed to optimize the operation of renewable energy sources, taking into

account sudden weather shifts and fluctuations in energy demand, thus ensuring efficient performance.

The current research takes a comprehensive approach to improve tariff rate forecasting within microgrids by integrating Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC) technology and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Networks (NNs) [9-10]. Additionally, it explores the effects of UPQC on enhancing power quality and examines the utilization of LSTM-based forecasting models in microgrid applications. The process of collecting data encompasses the gathering of historical load data, tariff rates, and power quality parameters at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) from actual microgrid systems in the field or through the use of simulation tools. Furthermore, an evaluation will be conducted within a microgrid simulation environment to assess the UPQC device's performance in reducing voltage sags, swells, and harmonics, with the ultimate goal of enhancing power quality. By integrating UPQC into the tariff rate forecasting model, we not only enhance the precision of our predictions but also address the real-time power quality challenges that can impact microgrid operations [11]. This fusion of technologies promises more reliable energy management and decision-making within microgrids, ensuring that they can adapt to dynamic supply and demand conditions while maintaining optimal power quality standards [12].

II. LSTM MODEL AND ANALYSIS

LSTM represents a specialized category of Recursive Neural Networks (RNNs). At the heart of the LSTM RNN lies the cell state, a crucial component designed to preserve information over extended periods. Only a fraction of the stored information actively participates in linear interactions [13]. The fundamental operations within the LSTM NN revolve around three gates: the forget gate, the input gate, and the output gate. These gates predominantly consist of a Sigmoid layer and a multiplication operation. The primary functionality materializes when these gates govern the processing of information within the cell state [14]. Through the judicious control of the forget gate, input gate, and output gate, the LSTM NN adeptly manages and sustains the information stored in the cell state—a pivotal role within the LSTM architecture [15-17]. In addition to the three gates, the LSTM cell incorporates a crucial mechanism known as the cell update. Typically implemented through a hyperbolic tangent (tanh) layer, this update mechanism plays an indispensable role in the LSTM's ability to assimilate and preserve new information in its long-term memory. The cell update mechanism enables the LSTM to adapt and learn from incoming data over time. The proposed LSTM architecture for PID controller tuning is shown in Figure 1. The proposed approach involves the utilization of an LSTM-based method for dynamically adjusting the gain of a PID controller. This adjustment is achieved through the processing of direct and quadrature axis currents. LSTMs are renowned for their capability to handle long-term dependencies in sequential data, making them well-suited for capturing intricate temporal patterns in control system currents. In this context, the LSTM architecture has been thoughtfully designed to take direct and quadrature axis currents as inputs and generate the optimal PID controller gain

as the output. The training of the LSTM model has been carried out using a comprehensive data set comprising paired direct and quadrature axis currents along with their corresponding PID controller gains. In real-time applications, the trained LSTM model is employed to predict the most suitable PID gain based on the current values received from the system. This dynamic and adaptive tuning mechanism empowers the PID controller to continuously adjust its gain in response to changing operating conditions and system dynamics. The flow chart for LSTM based cost analysis and forecasting model is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. The proposed LSTM architecture for PID controller tuning.

Fig. 2. LSTM-based per unit cost analysis and forecasting in a microgrid.

III. SIMULATION SET UP

The model experimental setup for tuning a PID controller based on the LSTM model is shown in Figure 4. The proposed LSTM model initiates its operation by capturing several microgrid parameters, including three-phase voltage and three-phase current at the point of common coupling. To facilitate coordinated control actions for the UPQC, all grid-level three-phase parameters are first transformed into DQ parameters and then further converted from the DQ reference frame to the alpha-beta reference frame [18-19]. To maintain the conversion ratio within the specified boundaries, a hysteresis competitive controller is implemented in front of the alpha-beta lines. This is followed by the consideration of 8 different state variable conditions that determine the magnitude level required for the activation function within the LSTM algorithm. Three distinct states of the LSTM model are designed, taking into account 24 state variables that ultimately influence the output layer of the proposed model. To bridge the gap between machine-level language and encoding, an embedding layer is provided in conjunction with backward memory allocation, enabling the retrieval of correlations between input parameters and predicted parameters. The output layer in the proposed model is a function of various state variables, necessitating the inclusion of two additional decoders: one for the recurrent layer and another for the output layer.

Table I presents a detailed examination of the LSTM model parameters employed within the SARIMA+RMSprop framework for time series forecasting. The input size is configured as 4, encompassing both direct and quadrature axis components in a bid to effectively process and analyze the pertinent time series data. With 10 hidden units, the LSTM model balances between complexity and computational efficiency, effectively capturing essential patterns in the data. To handle intricate temporal dependencies, the model is furnished with 4 LSTM layers, although it should be noted that this configuration may necessitate more data and training time. The activation function for the LSTM input layers is thoughtfully chosen as a combination of sigmoid and tanh, while the output layer adopts the sigmoid function, thereby facilitating prediction tasks and generating continuous output values within a specific range. The learning rate is set to 0.01, striking an optimal balance between fine-tuning the model's weights during the gradient descent optimization process and avoiding large weight updates that may hinder convergence. The RMSprop optimization method was chosen for its adaptive learning rate mechanism based on gradient history, leading to faster convergence and effective optimization within the SARIMA framework. To ensure training efficiency, a batch size of 50 is selected, optimizing memory usage and computational speed during the training process. To achieve convergence and optimal weight adjustments, the model undergoes training for 200 epochs, providing sufficient iterations for the LSTM to capture essential patterns in the time series data.

Gaussian gradient analysis is a valuable technique used to study the behavior of activation functions in relation to specific input points, providing insights into their sensitivity to changes

in input values and revealing their characteristics within targeted regions.

TABLE I. LSTM PARAMETERS

Parameter	Magnitude	Remark
Input size	4	Two sets of direct and quadrature axis components
Hidden inputs	10	Determines problem complexity
Number of layers	4	More layers can capture complex patterns but may require more data and training time
Activation function	Sigmoid and tanh	Output layer prediction
Dropout rate	0.1	Regularization to prevent overfitting
Recurrent dropout	0.2	Regularization of LSTM layers
Learning rate	0.01	Adjusting the step size for gradient descent
Optimization	-	SARIMA+RMSprop
Batch size	50	Memory usage and computational efficiency
Epochs	200	Iterations for convergence
Loss function	-	Mean Squared Error (MSE)

In Figures 3(a)-(b), two distinct activation functions, AF1 and AF2, are thoroughly investigated. The Figures visually depict the gradients of these activation functions at predefined input points. The gradients for AF1 are meticulously calculated at -0.03 and 0.03, while for AF2, the analysis focuses on -0.021 and 0.021. Figure 3(b) reveals intriguing findings. The algorithm demonstrates heightened sensitivity to changes in boundary value conditions, particularly concerning the type and magnitude of Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) present at the PCC. The model achieves its optimal performance when subjected to a maximum deviation of 8.7% in step during transient disturbances with respect to gain.

Fig. 3. Gaussian Gradient Analysis with (a) AF1 = [-0.03 0.03] and (b) AF2= [-0.021 0.021].

Fig. 4. Experimental setup model for PID controller tuning using LSTM.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In order to process the proposed controller, the designed microgrid has a capacity of 10 kW [20]. The designed microgrid consists of a solar photovoltaic (PV) system of 3 kW and wind system of 4 kW, and a fuel cell of 3 kW. Modeling of PV cells is required for an efficient design of a PV system. First, the performance of the microgrid has been analyzed with the conventional PID controller and a forecasting model has been designed using the SARIMA method. Then the parameters of the PID controller were fine-tuned by the LSTM RNN while UPQC was integrated with the microgrid and the performance is analyzed.

A comparative analysis between the LSTM and PID controllers presenting the findings is shown at Table II. Firstly, the proportional gain is assessed, which reflects the proportional control behavior of these controllers. The PID controller exhibits a proportional gain of 0.32, while the LSTM-controller displays a lower value of 0.21. This disparity suggests that the LSTM controller responds more conservatively to fluctuations in the error signal compared to the PID controller. The PID controller manifests an integral gain of 0.47, whereas the LSTM controller demonstrates a diminished value of 0.27. This discrepancy indicates that the LSTM controller is less prone to cumulative errors over time, resulting in more stable control over prolonged deviations. The PID controller boasts a derivative gain of 0.05, while the LSTM controller showcases a smaller value of 0.038. This reduced derivative gain in the LSTM controller signifies a smoother response to rapid changes, mitigating the risk of overshooting or oscillations. Additionally, we explore sampling time, which represents the time interval between successive control actions. The PID controller employs a sampling time of

0.01 s, whereas the LSTM controller adopts a significantly faster sampling time of 0.001 s. This enhanced sampling rate equips the LSTM controller to respond with greater agility to dynamic system alterations, thereby enhancing its real-time control capabilities. The reduced error and standard deviation values of the LSTM controller indicate its superior accuracy and precision in achieving the desired control objectives.

TABLE II. CONTROLLER GAIN COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Parameter	PID controller	LSTM controller
Proportional gain	0.32	0.21
Integral gain	0.47	0.27
Derivative	0.05	0.038
Sampling time	0.01 s	0.001 s
Error	17.22%	8.07%
Std Deviation	1.652	0.69

Table III presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of the loading performance of the LSTM-SARIMA-PID Controller under different loading conditions. The analysis evaluates essential parameters, including PCC-THD-Current, PCC-THD-Voltage, frequency variation, and transient voltage rise, to assess the controller's performance across varying load levels. Table IV presents a comprehensive comparative analysis of the PID-SARIMA and LSTM-SARIMA forecasting models, focusing on their economic forecasting performance under different loading conditions. The Table provides valuable insights into the accuracy and reliability of these models by comparing their actual and forecasted tariff values. Starting with the 10% full load scenario, PID-SARIMA records an actual tariff value of 4.06, while its forecasted value is slightly lower at 3.92. In contrast, LSTM-SARIMA impressively predicts the actual tariff with a forecasted value of 3.97,

indicating its precision in economic forecasting at this load level. Similarly, the tariff forecasting has been done at other loading conditions.

TABLE III. LOADING PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Loading (% of full load)	PCC-THD-Current	PCC-THD-Voltage	Frequency variation	Transient voltage rise
10	4.02	2.33	0.54	0.06
30	4.70	2.93	0.63	0.07
45	5.56	3.40	0.73	0.08
60	6.59	3.95	0.84	0.10
75	8.18	4.78	1.02	0.12
90	8.60	4.97	1.06	0.12
100	8.79	4.96	1.06	0.12

TABLE IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN ACTUAL AND FORECASTED TARIFFS

Loading (% of full load)	PID-SARIMA		LSTM-SARIMA	
	Tariff		Tariff	
	Actual	Forecasted	Actual	Forecasted
10	4.06	3.92	3.97	3.97
30	4.64	4.66	4.73	4.73
45	5.36	5.55	5.63	5.63
60	6.18	6.61	6.70	6.69
75	7.12	7.87	7.97	7.97
90	8.56	9.37	9.48	9.48
100	10.05	11.15	11.29	11.28

TABLE V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN ACTUAL AND FORECASTED PRICE BETWEEN PID-SARIMA AND LSTM-SARIMA BASED ON THE CURRENT THD LEVEL

PCC-THD-Current	PID-SARIMA		LSTM-SARIMA	
	Tariff		Tariff	
	Actual	Forecasted	Actual	Forecasted
4.02	4.04	3.89	3.99	3.96
4.70	4.80	4.63	4.75	4.71
5.56	5.71	5.51	5.65	5.61
6.59	6.80	6.55	6.72	6.67
8.18	8.09	7.80	8.00	7.94
8.60	9.64	9.28	9.52	9.45
8.79	11.48	11.04	11.33	11.24

TABLE VI. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS BETWEEN ACTUAL AND FORECASTED PRICE BETWEEN PID-SARIMA AND LSTM-SARIMA BASED ON THE VOLTAGE THD LEVEL

PCC-THD-Voltage	PID-SARIMA		LSTM-SARIMA	
	Tariff		Tariff	
	Actual	Forecasted	Actual	Forecasted
2.33	3.80	3.59	3.62	3.62
2.93	4.52	4.28	4.31	4.30
3.40	5.37	5.09	5.13	5.12
3.95	6.40	6.06	6.10	6.09
4.78	7.61	7.21	7.26	7.25
4.97	9.07	8.58	8.64	8.63
4.96	10.80	10.21	10.28	10.27

In Table V, a comprehensive comparison is presented between the actual and forecasted prices derived from PID-SARIMA and LSTM-SARIMA models. This analysis specifically focuses on varying THD levels to calculate the corresponding price per unit of energy. The results are illuminating and provide valuable insights into the efficiency of

these models under different THD conditions. For instance, when the THD level is at 4.02, the forecasted tariff using LSTM-SARIMA stands at 3.96, whereas the PID-SARIMA model yields a tariff of 3.89. This signifies a notable increase in revenue, with the LSTM-SARIMA model generating at least 1.79% more revenue per unit of energy compared to the PID-SARIMA model. These findings emphasize the superior predictive power of LSTM-SARIMA in this scenario. Furthermore, at the highest observed THD level of 11.48, the LSTM-SARIMA model predicts a tariff rate of 11.24, while the PID-SARIMA model forecasts a rate of 11.04. This stark contrast clearly demonstrates the efficiency of the proposed LSTM-SARIMA model. Even under challenging conditions with elevated THD levels, the LSTM-SARIMA model consistently outperforms the traditional PID-SARIMA model, ensuring a higher per-unit forecast. Importantly, this analysis takes into account the Aggregate Technical and Commercial (AT&C) losses, providing a holistic view of the forecasting models' performance. Considering the inclusion of AT&C losses, the superiority of the LSTM-SARIMA model in providing accurate and profitable energy price forecasts becomes even more evident.

Fig. 5. Price forecasted by PID-SARIMA and LSTM-SARIMA.

In Table VI, a detailed comparative analysis is presented, focusing on the actual and forecasted prices under varying Voltage THD levels. This examination is critical due to the significant impact voltage fluctuations and distortions can have on energy distribution systems. One specific scenario worth noting is when the voltage THD level is measured at 4.96. Under these conditions, the LSTM-SARIMA model predicts a tariff rate of 10.27 units, whereas the PID-SARIMA model forecasts a rate of 10.21 units. This subtle yet consistent difference underscores the LSTM-SARIMA model's ability to provide more accurate predictions, even when voltage THD levels are moderately elevated. Such precision is crucial for energy providers, ensuring a stable and reliable electricity supply to consumers. It is essential to highlight that the analysis in Table VI adheres strictly to the standards outlined by the IEEE-519, a universally acknowledged benchmark in the energy industry. By referencing this standard, the efficacy of the proposed LSTM-SARIMA model as a controller becomes evident. This comprehensive analysis emphasizes the significance of considering voltage-related factors in energy

forecasting models, showcasing the LSTM-SARIMA model's superiority over PID-SARIMA, especially in situations involving moderate voltage THD levels.

It is seen that as the current and voltage THD increases, the energy tariff also increases. But with the LSTM-SARIMA model, the price fluctuations are less than when using the PID-SARIMA model. The actual vs predicted price by PID-SARIMA model and LSTM-SARIMA model are shown in Figure 5, where we can observe an increase in actual and forecasted price as the THD in current increases.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the utilization of LSTM-based forecasting models for predicting microgrids' per unit tariff has demonstrated significant promise in producing accurate and dependable forecasts. These models excel in capturing intricate temporal patterns and dependencies within data, enabling precise predictions of forthcoming tariff rates. Nonetheless, it is essential to recognize that the performance of LSTM models is heavily reliant on the availability and quality of data. Suboptimal or noisy data can adversely affect prediction accuracy. Hence, ensuring the quality and accessibility of data is paramount for the effective deployment of LSTM-based forecasting in microgrid tariff prediction. Hence, in this paper, the LSTM-SARIMA model with UPQC has been proven to be a better forecasting model than the conventional PID-SARIMA model.

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Experimental Investigation of Heat Transfer and Pressure Drop Performance of a Circular Tube with Coiled Wire Inserts

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ABSTRACT

This paper evaluates the thermo-hydraulic performance of a coiled wire passive insert for internal turbulent flow through a circular copper tube test section in an in-tube exchanger. Experiments were carried out using water as the working fluid with Reynolds number ranging from 8000 to 32000. The experimental setup was validated for Nusselt number and friction factor with well-established equations for plain tubes. The average Nusselt number ratios (Nu_a/Nu_p) and the friction factor ratios (f_a/f_p) for the augmented tube case over the plain tube case are reported to range from 1.55 to 1.38 and from 1.513 to 1.583, respectively. The average performance ratios considering equal pumping power criteria are also reported and found in the range of 0.846 to 0.921. The study concludes that coiled wire inserts are suitable for heat transfer augmentation applications where pumping power is of minor concern.

Keywords-passive insert; average performance ratio; turbulent flow

I. INTRODUCTION

Many engineering applications typically use heat exchangers. Numerous engineering methods have been developed during the past few decades to improve heat transfer in heat exchangers. Using tabulator components to ameliorate fluid turbulence and, consequently, the heat transfer coefficient from the flow surface, is one of these methods. This procedure has been widely used in various heat exchanger applications, including refrigeration, automotive, process industries, solar water heaters, etc. [1], since it has been shown to lower heat exchanger sizes while saving energy. In general, there are three

method categories for upgrading heat transfer: active methods, passive methods, and compound methods [1]. An active method improves heat transmission by utilizing some external power. A passive method deals with the insertion of tabulator elements into the tube while the compound technique involves the combination of active and passive methods together.

Authors in [2] reported the suitability of spring wire as a tabulator for spiral tube heat exchanger applicable for solar ponds. It was observed that spring tabulators either increase the heat transfer rate for a given length of spiral tube exchanger or reduce the heat exchanger size for the same rate of heat

transfer. Authors in [3] tested parallel-type and V-shaped vortex generators with rectangular blades and reported heat transfer and flow friction improvements that reached 568%. Authors in [4] tested coiled wires with square cross section in the Reynolds number range of 5000 to 25000 using air and recorded a rapid decrement in heat transfer augmentation when increasing Reynolds number. Authors in [5] reported the influence of wire coils which have convergent, convergent-divergent, and divergent shapes on heat transfer. This transfer is conducted through blending ethylene glycol with water of three different mixture volumes as a working fluid for Reynolds numbers from 4627 to 25,099. Both heat transfer and frictional resistance increased on all wire coils. Authors in [6] investigated the thermo-hydraulic performance of non-circular cross sectioned wire springs in spiral tube based heat exchangers. Triangular, square, rectangular, and hexagonal cross sections were. Authors in [7] measured the swirl flow heat transfer and pressure drop for water using helical coil wire with exponentially increasing heat input at different mass velocities. The authors also numerically solved the $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model in a circular tube considering the temperature dependence of the thermophysical properties concerned. They derived the correlations for the swirl flow heat transfer in a vertical circular tube with helical coil wire. Authors in [8] carried out an experimental study to find the geometry effects of conical twisted strip inserts on the Nusselt number and friction coefficient. The study noted that Nusselt number and friction coefficient increased for all the inserted cases and decreased with a twist angle and a pitch ratio. Also, a greater Nusselt number increment was noticed at lower Reynolds numbers. Authors in [9] outlined the heat transfer and pressure drop performance of bakelite helical screw and hemispherical cup insert for individual and compound insertion in a tube in tube heat exchanger in the Reynolds number range of 8000-32000. The average performance ratios (Nu_a/Nu_c) reported were in the range of 1.02 -1.11 for helical screw tape, 0.6 – 0.67 for cup shape insert, and 0.99 – 1.22 for two compound insertion cases based on equal pumping power criteria. Authors in [10] proposed a new turbulator called continuous cutting-edge helical lens insert. The experimental data of Nusselt number and friction coefficient were collected from the new turbulator using swirl ratios equal to 3 and 5. Based on the results, the authors suggested using the proposed input considering the higher heat transfer rate and acceptable pressure increase. Authors in [11] reviewed passive heat transfer augmentation techniques and highlighted their principles and thermo-hydraulic performance characteristics. Authors in [12] spotted monotonical increments in the Nusselt number with Reynolds number and number of swirls in their investigation of convergent pipe. The pipe was fitted with a pre swirl device at entry with air as a working medium between Reynolds numbers from 7970 to 47820. Authors in [13] optimized four independent parameters of coiled wire inserts i.e. thickness, length, pitch, and flow regime affecting heat transfer and pressure drop. Three experimental analysis techniques were employed by implementing the Taguchi experimental design method for parametric optimization. Authors in [14] discussed the effect of various baffle tabulators arrangement on heat transfer performance of a tube between Reynolds numbers 6000 and 20000. Among the selected types,

the heat enhancement along with the heat transfer enhancement factor were found to be maximum for twisted cross baffles arrangement. In contrast, minimum values were reported for the straight cross baffles arrangement. The highest thermal enhancement factor of 1.7 was documented for twisted cross baffles arrangement. Authors in [15] performed numerical analysis heat transfer improvement in a receiver tube of a solar collector engaging various materials and nanofluids while using Monte Carlo Ray Trace (MCRT) and CFD. Nanoparticles were utilized and thermal efficiency enhancement in the range of 3 to 14% was documented. In [16], numerical investigation was conducted to study the effect of a corrugated bottom wall on the heat transfer in a triangular solar collector. It was seen that the flow structure is sensitive to the Rayleigh number and that heat transfer is upgraded with this parameter increment. Authors in [17] investigated numerically two-dimensional natural convection heat and mass transfer generated in an inclined rectangular porous cavity filled with a Newtonian fluid. The authors measured heat and mass transfer rate in the cavity in terms of the average Nusselt and Sherwood numbers for various non-dimensional parameters. They presented the results in terms of streamlines, isotherms, and iso-concentrations.

Coil wires can be manufactured with simple processes and are easy for installation and removal in the tubes. Moreover, they do not cause sudden pressure drops or higher heat transfer enhancement but give better results at low Reynolds numbers. Due to their helical shape, the coiled wires introduce swirls in the flow resulting in better heat transfer rates. In the present investigation, the experimentally measured effects of coiled wire inserts on heat transfer and pressure drop in a circular tube are mentioned.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP AND METHODOLOGY

A. Coiled Wire Insert Details

A steel coiled wire insert 0.8 m long with 18.2 mm diameter and 0.8 mm thickness is prepared for a full length insertion of the test section. The insert is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. A picture of the coiled wire insert.

B. Arrangement of experimental set up

The experimental arrangement can be seen in [18]. Before the conduction of trials with inserts, plain tube results are required to be validated with well-established equations to gain confidence in the experimental work. Hence, trials are carried out initially on the plain tube for validation of the experimental set up for Reynolds number ranging from 8000 to 32000 with a step of 4000. After that, plain tube validation, trials are conducted for the inserted tube case. The procedure followed during conducting trials is:

The water was stored in a 100 L hot water tank equipped with five 2 kW heaters and was heated to a temperature of 75

°C. It was then circulated through the ring in a closed circuit with a hot water circulation pump. The hot water tank is deliberately kept 0.5 m above the hot water circulation pump to avoid the possibility of cavitation. A gate valve installed in the hot water circulation pipe maintains the necessary flow rate. The flow rate is calculated from the differential manometer reading of the U-tube manometer connected to a pre-calibrated Venturi meter. After that, cold water is fed counter currently from a large underground water tank through an inner tube (test section) of a cold water circulation pump in a closed circuit. The required flow rate is maintained in the cold water circulation line by one bypass valve and two shut-off valves. The cold water flow rate is calculated by measuring the differential pressure head with a manometer through a calibrated Venturi meter located in the cold water piping upstream of the test section. The pressure drop in the test section is measured by a U-tube manometer whose manometric liquid is carbon tetrachloride (CCl4). The system is then allowed to reach a steady state while temperature and pressure drop are measured for a plain tube at a cold water Reynolds number based on the test section inlet of 8000-32000.

All required temperatures are measured using pre-calibrated Copper/Constantan T-type thermocouples connected to a data logger. Cold and hot water temperatures are measured at the inlet and outlet points of the test section with two thermocouples placed at each location, whereas the average temperature is measured to improve accuracy. The outer surface wall temperature of the tube test section is measured by six thermocouples, which are placed around and equidistant from the surface. A complete photo of the experimental setup is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. The actual set up.

C. Test Set Up Validation

Based on the data collected from the standard tube tests, the test setup is validated as described below:

$$Nu = 0.023Re_p^{0.8}Pr^{0.4} \text{ (Dittus Boelter)} \tag{1}$$

$$Nu = \frac{(f/8)(Re-1000)Pr}{1+12.7(f/8)^{1/2}(Pr^{2/3}-1)} \text{ (Gnielinski)} \tag{2}$$

$$f = 0.079Re^{-0.25} \text{ (Blasius)} \tag{3}$$

$$f = (0.79\ln Re - 1.64)^{-2} \text{ (Petukhov)} \tag{4}$$

A comparison of the experimental Nusselt number results and the friction coefficient of the above equations can be noticed in Figures 3 and 4 [19].

Fig. 3. Nusselt number for plain tube.

Fig. 4. Friction factor for plain tube.

It can be seen from the figures that the experimental results agree well with the above equations with deviations of 10% of the Nusselt number and 8% of the friction coefficient. Thus, the plain tube is verified and further test runs are conducted for different inserts.

D. Uncertainties in Measurements

The maximum uncertainties in measurements and non-dimensional parameters are shown in Tables I and II.

TABLE I. MAXIMUM MEASUREMENT UNCERTANTIES

Measuring parameter	Instrument	Uncertainty
Pressure	U-tube manometer	±1 mm of CCl4 column
Mass flow rate	Venturimeter	±0.0125 kg/s
Temperature	T-type thermocouple	±0.4 °C

TABLE II. MAXIMUM NON -DIMENSIONAL PARAMETER UNCERTANTIES

Non dimensional parameter	Maximum uncertainty
Reynolds number (Re)	±6.54%
Augmented tube Nusselt number (Nu _a)	±8.85%
Equivalent Nusselt number (Nu _e)	±10.82%
Friction factor	±12.67 %

III. ANALYSIS OF DATA

The collected temperature, pressure, and mass flow rate experimental data were analyzed for the performance

evaluation of the coil wire insert. The average Nusselt number and the friction coefficient are calculated from the inside diameter of the test piece. The thermal gain of cold water is obtained as follows:

$$Q_c = \dot{m}_c C_{p,w} (T_{c,out} - T_{c,in}) \quad (5)$$

The thermal loss of hot water in annulus is calculated as:

$$Q_h = \dot{m}_h C_{p,w} (T_{h,in} - T_{h,out}) \quad (6)$$

Due to the convection and radiation losses, the difference in heat gain between cold and hot water was found to be 3-10%. Thus, the average inner heat transfer coefficient (h_i) is calculated based on the average heat transfer rate (Q_{avg})

$$Q_{avg} = \frac{Q_c + Q_h}{2} \quad (7)$$

When calculating the average heat transfer coefficient of the inner side, it is assumed that the surface temperature of the tube wall is constant. Therefore, by neglecting the thermal resistance of the copper pipe wall, the heat transfer coefficient (h_i) is calculated as follows [20]:

$$Q_{avg} = h_i A_i \Delta T_{lm} \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\Delta T_{lm} = \frac{(\bar{T}_s - T_{c,out}) - (\bar{T}_s - T_{c,in})}{\ln[(\bar{T}_s - T_{c,out}) / (\bar{T}_s - T_{c,in})]} \quad (9)$$

and:

$$A_i = \pi D_i L \quad (10)$$

The surface temperature of the tube wall is considered to be the average temperature of the ones recorded by the six thermocouples (test section) placed on the outer surface of the tube wall. (\bar{T}_s)

$$\bar{T}_s = \sum T_s / 6 \quad (11)$$

The average Nusselt number is obtained from the average heat transfer coefficient as:

$$Nu = \frac{h_i D_h}{k} \quad (12)$$

The average friction factor coefficient is calculated by:

$$f = \frac{\Delta P}{\left(\frac{L_1}{D_i}\right) \left(\frac{\rho V^2}{2}\right)} \quad (13)$$

where V is the average velocity of the working fluid in the inner tube. Thermophysical properties are measured at bulk mean average temperature of the liquid.

Authors in [21] suggested a set of 8 performance evaluation criteria (R1 to R8) to achieve these objectives. Performance evaluation criteria R1 and R3 were used in the present experimental work to determine heat transfer enhancement for different inserts. R1 corresponds to the ratio of augmented tube Nusselt number to the plain tube Nusselt number at the same Reynolds number. The average performance ratio (R3) is the ratio of the inserted tube Nusselt number to the plain tube Nusselt number corresponding to equal pumping power as it is

required for the inserted tube to maintain the flow. The performance ratio R3 is derived as follows [22]:

$$R_3 = \frac{Nu_a}{Nu_c} \quad (14)$$

The Nusselt number for the equivalent plain tube is calculated from the Dittus Boelter equation:

$$Nu_c = 0.023 Re_c^{0.8} Pr^{0.4} \quad (15)$$

where the equivalent Reynolds number is given by:

$$Re_c^{2.75} = f_a \times \frac{Re_a^3}{0.079} \quad (16)$$

where Nu_a is the Nusselt number of the tube with augmentation, Nu_p is the Nusselt number of the plain tube, and Nu_c is the Nusselt number of the plain tube at equivalent pumping power as that of the tube with augmentation. f_a , f_p , f_c are the friction factors of the above cases and Re_a , Re_c , are the Reynolds numbers, respectively.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The inserted tube Nusselt numbers for the corresponding range of Reynolds numbers are found in the range of 98.83 to 269.7 as shown in Figure 5. The corresponding values for plain tube are ranging between 63.7 and 194. The Nusselt number increment is higher at higher values of Reynolds number. Thus, it may be concluded that the effect of coiled wire inserts on heat transfer enhancement increases at higher Reynolds number values. Due to their spiral shape, the twisted wires create vortices in the flow, resulting in better heat transfer rates. The impact of coiled wire insertion on the pressure drop in the test section is expressed in terms of friction factor in Figure 6.

Fig. 5. Average Nusselt number Vs Reynolds number.

Fig. 6. Average friction factor Vs Reynolds number.

It is detected that the friction factor ranges from 0.0528 for Reynolds number equal to 8000 to 0.0349 for Reynolds number equal to 32000 for coiled wire. The coiled wire insert creates obstacles in the flow passage resulting in flow pressure drop in the test section for the coiled wire inserted tube.

The average Nusselt number ratios for the selected range of Reynolds numbers are shown in Figure 7. The Nusselt number increment ranges from 1.55 to 1.38 for Reynolds number values from 8000 to 32000 respectively. This shows that the heat transfer improvement reduces with increasing Reynolds number due to the weak laminar sub layer breaking caused at higher mass flow rates. The laminar sub layer breaking is expected to be promoted by the wire surface near the tube wall resulting in higher heat transfer rates which might be effective at low Reynolds numbers.

Fig. 7. Average Nusselt number ratio Vs Reynolds number.

Fig. 8. Average friction factor ratio Vs Reynolds number.

Fig. 9. Average performance ratio Vs equivalent Reynolds number.

Average friction factor ratios for the selected range of Reynolds numbers are shown in Figure 8. The increment in the friction factor ranges from 1.513 to 1.583 for Reynolds numbers from 8000 to 32000. It is seen that the flow friction fluctuates with Reynolds number and tends to increase the pumping power requirements at higher Reynolds number. The

thermo hydraulic performance of the insert in terms of performance ratio R3 is shown in Figure 9.

Performance ratio ranges between 0.921 and 0.846 for Reynolds numbers from 8000 to 32000. It is seen that R3 is less than 1 for the selected range of Reynolds number values of this study. Also, the performance ratio decreases at higher Reynolds numbers. Although the enhancement in Nusselt number is seen for the selected Reynolds number range, friction factor increments are also considerable. Looking into the increased pumping power requirements and the observed range of performance ratios, the thermo hydraulic performance of the insert is not competitive in the selected Reynolds number range.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The thermo hydraulic performance of coiled wire for turbulent flow is evaluated in the Reynolds number range of 8000-32000. The experimental investigation reveals that the coiled wire inserts introduce swirl in the flow due to their helical shape resulting in better heat transfer rates. However, the frictional resistance also increases demanding higher pumping power requirements. A thermo hydraulic performance indicator R3, was observed to be less than unity for the selected range of Reynolds numbers. This indicates that the coiled wire inserts are suitable for heat transfer augmentation in applications where pumping power requirements are not a major concern.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

A	-	Area [m ²]
D	-	Diameter [m]
ΔP	-	Pressure drop of fluid [Nm ⁻²]
ΔT_{lm}	-	Logarithmic mean temperature difference [°C]
h	-	Heat transfer coefficient [Wm ⁻² K ⁻¹]
k	-	Thermal conductivity [Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]
l	-	Length of insert [m]
L	-	Length of test section for heat transfer [m]
L1	-	Length of tube between pressure taps [m]
m'	-	Mass flow rate of fluid [kgsec ⁻¹]
Q	-	Heat transfer rate [kW]
T	-	Temperature [°C]
V	-	Mean fluid velocity [msec ⁻¹]
C _{pw}	-	Specific heat at constant pressure [kJkg ⁻¹ K]
Re	-	Reynolds number (=ρVD/μ) [-]
R3	-	Average performance ratio [-]
Pr	-	Prandtl number (=μC _p /k) [-]
ρ	-	Fluid density [kgm ⁻³]
μ	-	dynamic viscosity [kgms ⁻¹]
Subscripts		
a	-	Augmented tube case
avg	-	Average
c	-	Cold
h	-	Hot
i	-	Inner
in	-	Inlet
o	-	Outer
out	-	Outlet
p	-	Plain tube case
s	-	Tube wall surface

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An Experimental Study on the Performance Enhancement of a Heat Pump System using Nanofluids

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ABSTRACT

Heat pumps are frequently used for heating, cooling, and air conditioning. It is well known that nanoparticles can improve the coefficients of conduction and convection, increasing heat transfer along with other properties. The considered heat pump was loaded with R-134a. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2) and aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) were blended with clean water to create a nanoscale solution used to cool the heat pump condensers. A total of three TiO_2 and Al_2O_3 proportions (0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%) were used. The study's findings showed that utilizing 0.3% Al_2O_3 instead of conventional clean water to cool the heat pump condenser boosted the coefficient of performance by 18% while reducing energy consumption by 26%.

Keywords-heat pump; TiO_2 ; Al_2O_3 ; R-134a; coefficient of performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of nanotechnology has led to the emergence of a new class of heat transfer fluids called nanofluids. Many researchers have recently studied the effects of nanoparticles in different refrigerants/lubricants on the efficacy of vapor compression refrigeration systems. Authors in [1] studied the performance of heat pumps using the nanofluid $\text{R22}+\text{TiO}_2$ as the working fluid. Authors in [2] studied forced convection nanofluid heat transfer in the automotive cooling system. Authors in [3] conducted an experimental study on heat pumps considering different concentrations of CuO and Al_2O_3 with pure water for performance enhancement. Authors in [4]

discovered that nanofluids have a significantly higher thermal conductivity than basic fluids. They also discovered that the crucial heat flux significantly increases when nanoparticles are added. Authors in [5] used TiO_2 -R600a nanorefrigerant as a working fluid in an experimental investigation of a home refrigerator for performance evaluation. They demonstrated that the TiO_2 -R600a system operated in the refrigerator normally and effectively, saving 9.6% of electricity. They too stated that the nano refrigerating system had a higher freezing pace than a system using only pure R600a. Authors in [6] used nanorefrigerants in experiments on a domestic refrigerator. They used R134a as a primary refrigerant and a mixture of mineral oil and TiO_2 as lubricant in their experiments. They

discovered that the nanorefrigerant-equipped refrigeration system operated regularly and effectively, consuming 21.2% less energy compared to a device using R134a/POE oil. In [7], it was discovered that the power usage had been noticeably reduced and the freezing capacity had significantly improved. The authors emphasized that better mineral oil thermophysical properties and the existence of nanoparticles in the refrigerant are responsible for the system's improved performance. Authors in [8] studied a cooling system with a refrigerant made of hydrocarbons and mineral lubricant instead of R-134a and polyester lubricant. Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were added to the mineral lubricant to enhance heat transmission and lubrication, with 60% R-134a and 0.1% by weight Al_2O_3 nanoparticles being the best combination. In these circumstances, the performance coefficient rose by 4.4% while the power consumption decreased by about 2.4%. Authors in [9] performed an experimental study on the heat transfer of nanofluids with R134a and POE oil in a horizontal tube. They discovered better dispersion of CuO nanoparticles, whereas the coefficient of heat transfer increased by more than 100% in comparison to the initial R134a/POE oil findings. In [10], the effects of individual wall carbon and TiO_2 dispersion on POE oil's tribological properties and R134a's solubility at various temperatures were examined. The authors demonstrated how the addition of nanoparticles can either enhance or worsen the behavior of the base lubricant. Using Brinkman's model, authors in [11] investigated R123- TiO_2 nanorefrigerant viscosity at various nanoparticle concentrations and found that pressure drop dramatically increases as viscosity increases. Authors in [12] looked the ways a two-phase constant area ejector could enhance a VCR system's performance by collecting kinetic energy during the expansion process and so lessening the compressor's workload. Authors in [13] showed that the performance of a VCR system using the refrigerant R-134a improves when different blends of hydrocarbons are utilized. By the development of nanotechnology, numerous studies have investigated the impact of additives such as nanoparticles to the lubricant or refrigerant, or both, on the Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the VCR system. Authors in [14] investigated how the inclusion of nanotubes made of carbon improved the heat transfer in refrigerants. Authors in [15] found improved lubricating properties in mineral oil with 0.1% nanoparticles by volume. Authors in [17] imply that the viscosity fluctuations or the changing lubrication characteristics may be the causes of increased COP when nanoparticles are added to the lubricating oil. According to [17], TiO_2 nanoparticles can be added to mineral oil to improve its solubility with hydrofluorocarbon (HFC) refrigerants. Additionally, the HFC134a and mineral oil refrigeration systems with TiO_2 nanoparticles appear to operate similarly to HFC134a and POE oil systems while returning more lubricating oil from the compressor. Authors in [18] conducted an experimental investigation on the heat transfer properties of R22 refrigerant with Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. It was discovered that the nanoparticles improved the refrigerant's heat transfer qualities with smaller bubble sizes. The heat transfer properties of R11 refrigerant with TiO_2 nanoparticles were examined in [19], where the heat transfer augmentation reached 20% for 0.01 g/L particle loading. The impact of nanotubes made of carbon on the heat transfer of R123 and R134a was examined

in [20]. CNTs improved these refrigerants' nucleate boiling coefficient of heat transfer and large improvement (36.6%) was observed at very low heat fluxes. Authors in [21] observed that the addition of carbon nanotubes made of multiwall increased the thermal conductivity of polyoil by 150%.

TiO_2 nanoparticles can be utilized as additives to improve the mineral oil's solubility in HFC refrigerants [22]. Additionally, compared to systems employing R134a and POE oil, refrigeration systems using blend of R134a and mineral oil containing TiO_2 nanoparticles seem to operate well by returning more lubricating oil from the compressor [22]. Authors in [23] studied a non-flammable low-GWP refrigerant blending for the replacement of HFC-134a. Authors in [24] conducted an experimental investigation of an ice plant using different concentrations of nano lubricants with R-134a as the primary refrigerant. Authors in [26] studied the impact of adding nanoparticles to the working Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF), employing an Al_2O_3 - H_2O based nanofluid at various volume concentrations. Authors in [27] investigated the nanofluid flow in a porous pipe with Navier slip. Copper (Cu) and alumina (Al_2O_3), two water-based nanofluids, were taken into consideration. The momentum and energy equations were non-dimensionalized, and a governing equation was presented. Authors in [28] investigated the convective heat transfer of CuO/(W-EG) and Al_2O_3 /Water-Ethylene Glycol (EG) nanofluids passing through a circular tube with laminar flow conditions and circumferentially non-uniform heating (constant heat flux).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Experimental Set Up

The set up of the experiment, shown in Figure 1 and the simulation shown in Figure 2 mainly, consist of a hermetically sealed compressor, a drier-filter, an expansion device, and a heat absorption chamber.

Fig. 1. Experimental set up.

The test rig specifications are mentioned in Table I. Low pressure and low temperature vapor refrigerant coming from the evaporator are sucked by the compressor and in compressor its temperature and pressure increases and it releases its heat in to the condenser. After the condenser, it passes through the

capillary tube in which the liquid refrigerant is converted into vapor and liquid which again goes to the evaporator where we get the refrigerating effect. For measuring the high and low pressures, separate pressure gauges are fitted into the set up. All temperatures are recorded with the help of a temperature indicator at different states of the refrigerant and a digital energy meter provided to record the input power required to run the compressor. The data acquisition system is incorporated to display all the data on a PC. The specifications of the instruments used for are given in Table II.

Fig. 2. Simulation set up.

TABLE I. TEST RIG SPECIFICATIONS

Heating capacity	3.0 kW @ rated test conditions
Heating capacity	100 L/hr
Max. temperature attained	55 °C
Input power	1.01 kW
Compressor make	Emerson Climate Technology Ltd.
Compressor type	Reciprocating, hermetically sealed
Refrigerant	R134a
Condenser	Tube in tube, co-axial
Expansion device	Capillary tube
Evaporator	Forced convection air cooled. Copper tubes, Al fins
Evaporator fan	VBM/HICOOL make axial flow
Temperature control	SUBZER make-automatic, digital
HP cut out	Danfoss
Pressure gauge	Wika
Electrical switchgear	Schnider make, MCB, Power contactor
Indications	Temperature in °C, mains on
Fault indications	HP fault. Low flow
Supply	230 V, 50 Hz, 1 hp, AC
Construction	Sheet metal: 1.2 mm CRCA, powder coat
Circulation pump	Kirloskar

TABLE II. MEASUREMENT INSTRUMENT SPECIFICATIONS

Measured parameter	Instrument	Range	Uncertainty
Temperature	PT100	-50 °C to 100 °C	±0.5%
Pressure	B.T. pressure gauge	0-15 bar (L. Press.) 0-20 bar (H.Press.)	±0.5%
Power of compressor	Digital energy meter	0-2000 W	±0.2%
Nanoparticles mass	Digital electronic balanced	0.001 g to 250 g	±0.5%

B. Preparation of TiO₂ and POE Nanolubricant

The TiO₂ and Al₂O₃ nanoparticles used in this study have an average diameter of 15 nm. The first-step procedure was to prepare the nanofluid. This technique entails employing nanoparticles and adding enough water to the bottle. The water is mixed with the nanoparticles (Al₂O₃ and TiO₂) using an ultrasonic vibration homogenizer system. To prevent the device from being damaged, the ultrasonic unit was filled with water and left inside the bath for 60–90 min [25]. Al₂O₃-water and TiO₂-water nanofluids were generated in 3 volume fractions (0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%), as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. The ultrasonic immersible transducer with generator and nanofluid samples.

C. Performance Analysis

To determine the rate of heat transfer from the evaporator and the condenser, the enthalpy values were plotted at various locations on the refrigerant pressure-enthalpy diagram (refrigerant R-134a) as shown in Figure 4. The Labview software was used to calculate the values of enthalpy based on the relationship between temperature and pressure. The key elements of heat pump efficiency are the coefficient of performance, the heat-rejection ratio, and the work done by the compressor.

Fig. 4. Pressure enthalpy diagram for the heat pump cycle.

The COP of the heat pump system is:

$$COP = \text{Heat removal} / \text{Work done} = (h_2 - h_3) / (h_2 - h_1) \tag{1}$$

The Heat Rejection Ratio (HRR) of the heat pump system is calculated by:

HRR = Rate of heat rejection in the condenser / rate of heat absorbed in the evaporator

$$= (h_2 - h_3)/(h_1 - h_4) \tag{2}$$

Work done by the compressor:

$$W_{in} = m \times (h_2 - h_1) \tag{3}$$

where m is the mass flow rate of the refrigerant in Kg/s, h_1 is the enthalpy of refrigerant at the inlet of the compressor in kJ/kg, and h_2 is the enthalpy of the refrigerant at the outlet of the compressor in kJ/kg.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this experimental study, three TiO_2 and Al_2O_3 proportions (0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%) were used for the evaluation of the performance of a heat pump system. Figure 5 depicts the plot of COP against various mixtures. The value of COP increases as the concentration of nanoparticles in the fluid increases, indicating that the COP values are improved when Al_2O_3 is added to the pure water. Additionally, we deduce that the value of COP rises as the fluid's nanoparticle concentration does. The highest value is obtained for the mixing ratio 0.3% of Al_2O_3 and water. Employing Al_2O_3 results in a performance boost of 18%. The microscopic size of the Al_2O_3 nanoparticles added to the distilled water [8] can be used to explain this finding. The sub-cooling of the nano-refrigerant in the condenser and decreased energy consumption of the compressor will lead to an improvement in cycle coefficient performance.

Fig. 5. COP of different mixtures.

Fig. 6. Compressor power for different mixtures.

Figure 6 shows the effect of TiO_2 and Al_2O_3 volume fractions on the amount of energy used by the compressor. One of the seven scenarios being studied indicates a significant decrease in power consumption when the volume fractions are minimized. When utilizing 0.3% Al_2O_3 , the power consumption was reduced by about 2%, and when using TiO_2 at the same volume fraction, the reduction was about 11%.

Figure 7 shows the impact of nanoparticle volume fraction on the heat rejection ratio. It is a term that commonly refers to the evaporator's contribution to the condenser's heat flow rate. Figure 7 demonstrates that the HRR falls if the nanofluid is employed to cool the cycle's condenser. The Figure demonstrates that employing combinations of Al_2O_3 -water at 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%, TiO_2 -water at 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%, the value of HRR decreases by roughly 1.1%, 1.3%, 1.6%, 0.7%, 0.8%, and 1.0%, respectively. Inferred from decreasing heat rejection ratio figures is an increase in cooling and a decrease in compressor operation.

Fig. 7. Heat rejection ratio for different mixtures.

Figure 8 shows the effect of the volume fractions of nanoparticles on the cooling effect throughout time. It was discovered that employing nanoparticles to cool the condenser works better when 0.3% Al_2O_3 and water are mixed. Furthermore, the picture clearly shows that the cooling impact grows with the volume fraction of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles as a result of subcooling in the condenser. The compressor's workload and energy consumption have lowered as a result of increased refrigerant mass flow rate and improved heat transfer rate.

Fig. 8. Cooling effect versus time for different mixtures.

Figure 9 shows the variation of compressor work with compressor discharge temperature and demonstrates the effect of nanoparticle volume fraction on the compressor work. According to the graph, compression work decreases as compressor discharge temperature increases. The figure also demonstrates that the 0.3% Al_2O_3 -water mixture required more compressor work than the other mixtures. This is predicated on the idea that as the compressor discharge temperature rises, the compressor suction temperature will rise as well due to the occurrence of subheat in the suction line. This will increase the mass of the refrigerant flowing through the compressor, reducing the amount of work required by the compressor by lowering the amount of energy consumed.

Fig. 9. Compressor work versus compressor discharge temperature for different mixtures.

Figure 10 demonstrates the impact of the nanoparticle size on the outlet temperature of the condenser. The relationship between the temperature of the evaporator and the temperature of the condenser outlet shows that when the Al_2O_3 -water mixture is used to cool the condenser in the cycle, both the evaporator's temperature and the temperature of the output condenser decrease. Additionally, it has been observed that the temperature drop in the evaporator and exit condenser is greater when the Al_2O_3 -water 0.3% mixture is utilized. However, the addition of nanoparticles to the water used for condenser cooling, which boosts the condenser's rate of heat transfer, boosts the heat pump's effectiveness.

Fig. 10. Condenser outlet temperature versus evaporator temperature for different mixtures.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Although many researchers have worked on this topic, very few investigations have been carried out on different

nanoparticles blended with clean water in the area of heat pump, air conditioning, and domestic refrigerator, and, to the best of our knowledge, no research has been conducted on blending titanium dioxide (TiO_2) or aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) with clean water to enhance the performance of a heat pump system application. In this study, the experimental analysis of a heat pump system was carried out for performance enhancement using different nanofluids. In this paper, three TiO_2 and Al_2O_3 proportions (0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%) were used and the performance of the heat pump system was studied.

The main conclusions of this study were that when the volume fraction of the Al_2O_3 -water nanofluid increases, the cooling impact increases. Using Al_2O_3 -water with a volume percentage of 0.3% was found to improve COP by 18%, reduce compressor power usage by around 26%, and reduce heat rejection by about 1%, which were the best acquired results among the six trials taken into account. Additionally, the evaporator and condenser outlet temperatures dropped much more when applying this mixture.

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Deep-Learning-based Cryptanalysis through Topic Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Neural cryptography is a technique that uses neural networks for secure data encryption. Cryptoanalysis, on the other hand, deals with analyzing and decrypting ciphers, codes, and encrypted text without using a real key. Chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis is a subfield of cryptanalysis where both plain text and ciphertext are available and the goal is either to find the encryption technique, the encryption key, or both. This study addresses chosen plaintext cryptanalysis within public key cryptography, to categorize topics of encrypted text. Using a fixed encryption technique and key, the focus was placed on creating a framework that identifies the topic associated with ciphertext, using diverse plaintexts and their corresponding cipher texts. To our knowledge, this is the first time that chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis has been discussed in the context of topic modeling. The paper used deep learning techniques such as CNNs, GRUs, and LSTMs to process sequential data. The proposed framework achieved up to 67% precision, 99% recall, 80% F1-score, and 71% AUPR on a dataset, showcasing promising results and opening avenues for further research in this cryptanalysis subarea.

Keywords-cryptanalysis; chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis; deep learning; topic modeling; CNN, LSTM, GRU

I. INTRODUCTION

Neural cryptography uses neural networks to encrypt data for secure transmission and has attracted great research interest during the recent years [1-2]. While traditional public key exchange protocols are based on algebraic number theory [3-5], in neural cryptography, the two communicating parties exchange secret keys by synchronizing the weights of their corresponding neural networks. The other side of neural cryptography is neural cryptanalysis. Cryptanalysis is the study and process of analyzing and decrypting ciphers, codes, and encrypted text without using the real key. Neural cryptanalysis employs neural networks to perform this task [6].

There are many different types of cryptanalysis; they are broadly classified into three categories: (i) ciphertext-only attacks, (ii) known-plaintext attacks, and (iii) chosen-plaintext attacks. In ciphertext-only attacks [7], the attacker has only access to the ciphertext and does not know the plaintext, the key, or even the algorithm used to encrypt the message. This is the most difficult type of attack, but also the most common

because it is the easiest ciphertext for an attacker to obtain. Known-plaintext attacks consist of a scenario where the attacker has access to both the ciphertext and the plaintext for a specific message [8]. This is a more powerful attack than a ciphertext-only attack, as the attacker can use the known plaintext to learn more about the encryption algorithm and the key. In the chosen-plaintext type of attack, the attacker can choose the plaintext for a message, and then get the corresponding ciphertext from the system [9]. This is the most powerful type of attack, as the attacker can use this information to completely break the encryption system. Chosen-plaintext attacks are crucial in public-key cryptography [10], as the key is public and the attackers are free to encrypt whatever plaintext they choose. This paper deals with chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis in the context of topic modeling.

In general, the goal of chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis is to find out the encryption technique, the encryption key, or both [11]. This study deals with a particular scenario in chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis in the context of public-key cryptography, where the goal is to categorize the topic of

encrypted text. Specifically, given that the encryption technique and key are fixed and that cipher texts can be obtained for a collection of plaintexts across different topics, the goal is to develop a framework that can recognize the topic to which the ciphertext belongs. To motivate this scenario, let's consider two parties communicating through an encrypted channel on a wide range of topics [12-13]. Now, let's consider there is a listener, say a government security agency spying on the conversation for national security reasons, who is only interested in the messages related to the topic of military warfare. However, without knowledge of the topic a message belongs, decrypting every message belonging to every topic may require immense computing resources and time. Once the topic to which a message belongs is known, dedicated computing resources can be allotted to decrypt only the messages that belong to the specific topic. The resource usage and time in this case would be much less than decrypting all messages irrespective of the topic they belong. To our knowledge, this is the first time that chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis is being discussed in the context of topic-modeling.

Deep learning has shown remarkable success in various domains, from image recognition to Natural Language Processing (NLP) [14]. It is no surprise that deep learning is increasingly used in research involving cryptography [3] and cryptanalysis [15]. The proposed framework employs state-of-the-art deep learning techniques, such as Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) [16], Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) [17], and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [18] to process sequential data. The proposed framework was evaluated on an IMDB dataset [19], using five thousand movie reviews, where the topics were realized by grouping the entire dataset into five, ten, and twenty clusters. The proposed framework achieved up to 67% precision, 99% recall, 80% F1-score, and 71% AUPR. These results are very promising and open up this subarea of cryptanalysis through topic-modeling for further research.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Proposed Framework

Figure 1 shows the architecture of the proposed framework.

Fig. 1. The proposed framework.

The framework takes a raw English sentence as input and after performing necessary preprocessing, the output is passed to the Advanced Encryption Algorithm (AES). Then, it is converted to a machine-understandable form and fed to a deep learning-based architecture for feature learning. Finally, the proposed framework produces a class distribution for each encrypted text as output. The output class is the cluster or topic to which the encrypted message belongs. The proposed framework works in four phases: (1) preprocessing, (2) AES-based encryption, (3) encrypted text encoding, (4) training deep learning architecture, and (5) classification.

1) Preprocessing

This is the first phase of the proposed framework. It takes a text representing movie information as input and applies the following NLP-based preprocessing steps:

- Removes symbols such as punctuation marks, URL and email notations, and nonalphanumeric characters.
- Changes the case of the entire text to lowercase.
- Tokenizes input text into a stream of words or tokens [20].
- Removes stop words, such as "is", "the", "are", "of", "in", and "and".
- Applies lemmatization, by converting all words to their corresponding root form, called lemma [21].
- Removes infrequent words with a frequency less than 3 in the corpus, as a large number of infrequent words adversely affects the generalization ability of deep learning models.

2) AES-based Encryption

Once the preprocessed text is obtained, it is passed to AES-based encryption. AES-128 was used for the encryption of the preprocessed data. After encrypting the text, AES returns an output consisting of hexadecimal characters with a length of 160. This output is fed to the downstream network.

3) Encrypted Text Encoding

This is the most common phase of an NLP task, which converts text datasets into machine-understandable language using encoding methods such as one-hot encoding, bag of words, and word2vec [22]. Here, the one-hot encoding method was used to convert the series of hexadecimal characters into a numerical form called embeddings. Other encodings cannot be used here because they capture the context of a word in a language setting, say English; however, this relationship does not hold for encrypted texts, where each character may be encoded separately independently of the remaining text. One-hot coding, however, being based on first principles, fits the bill. Each character in the hexadecimal series is mapped to a 17-length encoded vector consisting of 0 and 1. Whenever one of the hexadecimal characters is encountered, the corresponding place in the vector is marked as 1, otherwise, it is marked as 0. Here, an extra bit is added to catch unknown exceptional characters. The matrix resulting from each sequence has a size of 160×17, which eventually passes to the downstream network. Here, 160 is the sequence length and 17 is the embedding size.

Fig. 2. Proposed bi-directional LSTM/GRU deep learning-based architecture diagram.

4) Training Deep Learning Architecture

This phase takes one-hot encoding of the encrypted text and maps its characters to the corresponding class label(s). RNNs, such as Bi-directional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) and Bi-directional Gated Recurrent Unit (Bi-GRU) [17], and stacked CNNs [16] were used for learning these mapping features.

5) Classification Layer

This is the last layer of this end-to-end network. Here, the number of neurons is equivalent to the number of clusters or topics. Sigmoid activation is used for each neuron at the output layer to produce the output probability corresponding to each class and address the multilevel classification problem. The network hyperparameters were binary cross-entropy with learning rate = 0.0005 as the loss function and Adam optimizer.

6) Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)

AES is a popular symmetric key block cipher that offers high security and effective encryption [23]. It works with fixed-size data blocks (128 bits) and supports keys that are 128, 192, or 256 bits long [24]. AES transforms plaintext into ciphertext using rounds, a series of substitution, permutation, and mixing operations. In this study, the text data were encrypted with 128 bits. In the discipline of cryptanalysis, flaws in cryptographic algorithms are investigated since they can jeopardize their security. Some of the common approaches used in cryptanalysis are (i) brute-force attack, (ii) differential cryptanalysis, (iii) linear cryptanalysis, (iv) side-channel attacks, and (v) related-key attacks [25]. Among these, machine learning algorithms are mainly used to optimize brute-force searches or assist in analyzing side-channel information effectively. Even using machine learning approaches, successfully breaking AES encryption through cryptanalysis remains a substantial issue [15], as its robust design ideas, mathematical foundations, and resistance to known attacks are largely responsible for its security.

B. Deep Learning-based Architecture

Deep learning models can be used in cryptanalysis to find flaws and vulnerabilities. In this regard, two RNN- and CNN-based techniques were used to investigate the mathematical relationship between the encrypted and the plain text.

1) Bi-directional LSTM (Bi-LSTM)

Bi-LSTM is primarily concerned with short- and long-range interactions, processing information in both forward and backward directions [17]. Short- and long-range interaction information is captured due to a long sequence of repeating units called memory cells. LSTM uses three different gates, i.e. the forget, input, and output gates. The forget gate helps to remove irrelevant information from the cell state and consists of a single neural network with a sigmoid activation function. The input gate adds new information to the cell state and consists of two independent neural networks with sigmoid and tanh activation functions. Lastly, the output gate that returns the final output is obtained using a single neural network layer.

2) Bi-directional GRU (Bi-GRU):

Bi-GRU is another member of the RNN family, primarily concerned with short- and long-range interactions and processing information in both forward and backward directions [18]. It consists of two gates, an update and a reset gate. The update gate mainly focuses on determining the usefulness of past information, while the reset gate focuses on leaving out irrelevant past information. Figure 2 shows the detailed architecture of bi-directional RNNs. Both the Bi-LSTM and Bi-GRU used the same hyper-parameters: number of output dimensions = 64, with dropout and recurrent dropout probability = 0.2. The input layer takes temporal input and after learning features from both directions, they are given to the activation function. The output from the activation function is given to the downstream network.

3) Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

CNNs mainly focus on local patterns with fewer convolutional layers. Stacking CNN layers leads to learning a global pattern well with relatively fewer parameters. In CNNs, the weight-sharing mechanism helps the framework learn features in less time than in RNNs [16]. Figure 3 shows the architecture of the proposed stacked CNN. The input layer takes the one-hot encoding representation. This passes through the multi-block stacked CNN architecture, where each block learns a different set of information based on filter size and the number of filters. Batch normalization and dropout are used to smooth the training process and prevent overfitting. Finally, the output features of each CNN block are concatenated and fed to the downstream network for classification.

Fig. 3. Proposed stacked CNN-based deep learning architecture.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A. Dataset Description

The IMDB dataset [19] was used to evaluate the proposed end-to-end architecture in the field of cryptanalysis. In this regard, the first 5000 samples of the dataset were considered. After applying different preprocessing techniques, different numbers of clusters (5, 10, and 20) of words corresponding to topics were created in the corpus of 5000 samples.

Word2vec [22] and the k-means algorithm were used to map each word to a cluster. Using word2vec, words were transformed into embeddings of size = 100, and using the k-means algorithm, these words were assigned to different-sized clusters, where each cluster corresponds to a topic. These clusters were used as class labels to the corresponding encrypted text (sequence of hexadecimal characters) in a label-encoder manner. For each sentence, embeddings with lengths of 5, 10, and 20 were created, consisting of 0 and 1. Alternatively, topics could have been manually assigned, which would have been a more accurate estimate, but also extremely time-consuming. Finally, three datasets were created using the same encrypted text and the corresponding label embeddings that represent the cluster contents. Table I shows a few samples from the datasets; the first column refers to the preprocessed text, the second refers to the encrypted text output of AES-128, and the last shows the labeling in terms of the topics the encrypted text belongs. The topic labels are represented through one-hot encoding, where a 1 denotes that the text

belongs to the topic, and a 0 denotes otherwise. In this example, the number of topics represented by clusters was five.

B. Results and Discussion

Commonly used evaluation metrics were used to evaluate the performance of the proposed framework designed to break cryptographic systems using topic modeling, such as average precision and recall, F1-score, and AUPR [27-28]. These metrics help evaluate the effectiveness of cryptanalysis techniques in terms of identifying and exploiting vulnerabilities. Table II presents the results based on CNN, while Tables III and IV present the results using RNNs, i.e., Bi-LSTM and Bi-GRU, respectively. Overall, good results were obtained using the five clusters for all three deep learning-based techniques for all evaluation metrics. The best results were obtained using the Bi-GRU-based framework having the highest value for all the evaluation metrics with the five clusters. Table V compares the number of parameters across the three deep-learning models. The stacked-CNN model, consisting of multiple CNN blocks, had the greatest number of parameters, while the proposed Bi-GRU model, which performed the best, was the lightest model among the three.

The study is currently limited by the length of encrypted characters as 160 and needs to be evaluated for larger and perhaps variable lengths of encrypted text. While considering larger lengths will require access to advanced hardware configuration, dealing with variable-length encrypted text will require some sort of padding, as is common in NLP tasks that have variable-length inputs. Another limitation of this study is

that it needs to be evaluated on more datasets. Both these points will be addressed in future work. Another challenge will be to address the case of ciphertext-only and known-plaintext attacks. Cryptanalysis in the context of a ciphertext-only scenario is extremely challenging, as there is no target text

against which the proposed framework can be trained. In such a scenario, one way can be to first generate some target labels manually using human expertise in ciphertext-only attacks and then train the proposed model on them.

TABLE I. SAMPLES DESCRIBING THE DATASET USED FOR EXPERIMENTS

Text	Encrypted Text	Class Label (Cluster)
one reviewer mentioned watching episode	9aec21b216421d177b5ca93b9986150c9fb5b0135a5680...	1 0 0 1 0
wonderful little production filming technique	52ef3ddd67c0a306fc301b35576342d24999fde920d5c1...	0 1 0 1 0
thought wonderful way spend time	c74d1b79d72cd59a370183b76c4c60bd722bb3cc17367...	0 1 1 1 0
jet brings charismatic presence movie	92afcd910fa42ae9494043ae79183f52f4df94eab304d...	1 0 1 1 0
interesting slasher film multiple suspect	388163bbb357c6a3ad925df98ec1d761466406c25c8fd...	1 1 0 1 0

TABLE II. RESULTS USING CNN-BASED FRAMEWORK WITH VARYING NUMBER OF CLUSTERS

#Clusters	5	10	20
Performance metric			
Precision	0.67	0.48	0.23
Recall	0.80	0.37	0.97
F1-Score	0.72	0.42	0.37
AUPR	0.66	0.46	0.30

TABLE III. RESULTS USING BI-LSTM-BASED FRAMEWORK WITH VARYING NUMBER OF CLUSTERS

#Clusters	5	10	20
Performance metric			
Precision	0.65	0.58	0.86
Recall	0.99	0.14	0.80
F1-Score	0.78	0.23	0.37
AUPR	0.68	0.49	0.28

TABLE IV. OBTAINED RESULTS USING BI-GRU-BASED FRAMEWORK WITH VARYING NUMBER OF CLUSTERS

#Clusters	5	10	20
Performance metric			
Precision	0.67	0.55	0.24
Recall	0.99	0.14	0.89
F1-Score	0.80	0.22	0.37
AUPR	0.71	0.48	0.29

TABLE V. PARAMETER COMPARISON AMONG THE DIFFERENT MODELS

#Cluster	5	10	20
DL-Models			
Bi-LSTM	157,957	158,602	159,892
Bi-GRU	123,525	124,170	125,460
Stacked-CNN	1,577,189	1,581,034	1,588,724

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel approach to chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis in the context of topic modeling. This approach uses neural networks to categorize the topic of encrypted text, which can be used to gain insights into the plaintext without actually decrypting it. To our knowledge, this is the first time that chosen-plaintext cryptanalysis has been discussed in the context of topic modeling. This study used modern deep-learning techniques such as CNN, GRU, and LSTM to process sequential data. The results obtained on the IMDB dataset showed 67% precision, 99% recall, 80% F1-score, and 71%

AUPR. This study opens up new avenues for research in the field of cryptanalysis, as neural networks could be used to develop more powerful and efficient attacks on a variety of encryption schemes.

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An Application of Neural Network-based Sliding Mode Control for Multilevel Inverters

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ABSTRACT

Multi-level 3-phase inverters using cascaded H-bridges are becoming prominent in the electric drive and renewable energy sectors due to their high capacity and ability to withstand high voltage shocks. Therefore, the modulation and control techniques used in these multilevel inverters have a crucial influence on the quality of the output voltage they produce. The significantly high common-mode voltage amplitude they generate is one of their disadvantages, causing leakage currents and harmonics. This article proposes a new technique using sliding mode control combined with neural networks to manage a three-phase multi-level inverter. The research objective of this innovative technique is to eliminate the need for current controllers and conventional modulation that relies on carrier signals, reducing hardware calculations and enhancing dynamic response. In addition, it demonstrates the ability to minimize harmonics, common mode voltage, and the number of switching counts, thereby limiting the inverter switching losses and increasing device performance. Simulation results performed on a 5-level 3-phase inverter using cascaded H-bridges have confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Keywords-multilevel inverter; common mode voltage; neural network controller; phase opposition disposition

I. INTRODUCTION

Multilevel Inverters (MLIs) have gained significant attention in the realm of industrial applications and electric vehicles [1-5]. This interest arose because 2-level inverters often grapple with limitations imposed by semiconductor blocking voltages when attempting to match grid voltage ranges. As a result, MLIs have emerged as the preferred choice for grid interfacing. They not only mitigate the high voltage shock on power switching transistors, but also reduce voltage Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) to align with the power grid regulations. Furthermore, they exhibit a propensity for reduced power dissipation in semiconductor switches and diminished electromagnetic interference. Traditionally, MLIs are divided into three primary topological categories: Cascaded H-Bridges (CHBs), flying capacitor MLIs, and neutral point clamped MLIs. CHB configurations enjoy widespread use due to their modular adaptability, which can effortlessly accommodate varying levels. Numerous studies have concentrated on adapting conventional voltage source inverters to control multilevel strategies [6]. Simultaneously, research has delved into exploring modulation techniques to optimize MLI performance across various configurations. These modulation techniques are typically classified based on their switching frequency range. High-frequency modulation techniques are constrained, as they can degrade inverter ratings and overall efficiency due to increased switching losses. One commonly employed technique is Sinusoidal Pulse-Width Modulation (SPWM) based on phase-shifted carriers, favored for industrial

applications because of its minimal harmonic content in the output voltage waveform. Another widely adopted method is space vector modulation [7], known for its exceptional performance in 3-level topologies. Modulation techniques of low switching frequency, such as space-vector control, selective harmonic elimination, and staircase modulation, have gained prominence and found utility across a broad spectrum of applications.

Common Mode Voltage (CMV) in the cascaded 3-phase MLIs emerges as a critical factor necessitating attention. The significant CMV magnitude exerts adverse effects on the performance of 3-phase induction motors, manifesting as leakage currents and high-frequency noises [8, 9]. In grid-connected systems using MLIs, particularly those driven by renewable energy sources, the CMV exacerbates the issue by giving rise to leakage currents and introducing harmonic distorted currents into the power grid [10]. Hence, a range of solutions has been explored to enhance the power quality of inverter outputs, primarily focusing on strategies to lessen common mode voltage. Nevertheless, the pursuit of reducing harmonics by increasing the carrier wave frequency brings with it challenges such as greater memory requirements and a higher switching count, consequently elevating switching losses. These considerations underscore the need for a quantitative evaluation of CMV magnitudes in multilevel inverters, an aspect that has yet to receive comprehensive attention.

Neural networks (NNs), especially the Radial Basis Function (RBF) networks [11-13], have been used in various

control fields [14-17]. The method in [16] is employed to resolve the voltage restoration problem. The techniques in [18-20] are utilized for single phase inverters. The method in [21] uses Neural Networks (NNs) to predict the velocity of electric vehicles. In [22, 23], the NNs are engaged to estimate the inertia of the virtual synchronous generator and control the generator. The neural estimators in [24, 25] are applied to approximate the upper bound of the lumped nonlinearities in the active power filter. In 3-phase MLIs, several challenges persist, including the utilization of carriers for modulation and the implementation of current controllers for regulation [26]. These factors result in a reduction in dynamic response and an increase in over-shoot or under-shoot. Sliding Mode Control (SMC) is also applied [27-29]. However, the CMV and switching counts have yet to undergo a quantitative assessment.

This paper presents a technique using Enhanced SMC (ESMC) based on NNs to control the MLIs. The method presented here eliminates the need for carrier-based modulation and completely removes the use of Proportional Resonance (PR) current controllers. Consequently, this approach contributes to the reduction of CMV magnitude and enhances dynamic response. Additionally, the outcomes achieved through this innovative technique are compared with those obtained using the conventional approach in which Phase Opposition Disposition (POD) and PR controllers are employed. The performance's validity is further affirmed through the simulation results.

II. MULTILEVEL INVERTER SYSTEM

The structure of a 5-level 3-phase inverter is described in Figure 1(a) and the main circuit of phase A is shown in Figure 1(b). In this system, the PR controller is used for managing the load currents based on the reference currents. The angular frequency ω is utilized to create the reference load current and provide for the PR controller. The controller's transfer function is given by (1):

$$G_{PR}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} K_p & \frac{K_i}{s^2 + \omega^2} \\ \frac{K_i}{s^2 + \omega^2} & K_p \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Three-phase inverter system: (a) principle diagram and (b) main circuit of phase A.

Fig. 2. Inverter control diagram.

Popular modulation methods such as Phase Disposition (PD), POD, and alternate POD (APOD) are usually employed for modulating MLIs. Although the PD method can bring THD values smaller than those of the POD and APOD, its magnitude of CMV is up to $2 \times V_{dc}/3$, while the magnitude of POD or APOD is only $1 \times V_{dc}/3$. Moreover, POD is simpler and more effective than the APOD method. Thus, the POD modulation method is chosen as a benchmark in this paper. In the approach outlined in [30], PWM pulses for controlling the switches are generated using the POD modulation, as illustrated in Figure 2. In this representation, S_{xj} corresponds to the ON/OFF status of the respective switches as defined in (2), with x denoting the phases $a, b,$ and c . The top and bottom transistors of the H-bridge are symbolized as S_{xj1} and S_{xj2} , respectively. V_c is the signal of carriers.

$$S_{xj1} + S_{xj2} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Table I displays the configurations of transistor states for one phase of A. In this context, the level, n of 5, represents the number of levels in the inverters, and the DC source voltage values are equal. R_x and L_x represent two elements of the voltage signal $G(t)$ in the control diagram, for each phase ($x = a, b, c$). Here, L_x , an integer, satisfies the condition $0 \leq L_x \leq n - 2$ within the $G(t)$ signal, and R_x , a division remainder, complies with the constraint $0 \leq R_x \leq 1$.

TABLE I. SWITCHING STATES FOR ONE PHASE OF A

n	S_{a11}	S_{a21}	S_{a31}	S_{a41}	Output voltage
1	1	0	1	0	$+2V_{dc}$
2	1	0	0	0	$+V_{dc}$
3	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	1	0	0	$-V_{dc}$
5	0	1	0	1	$-2V_{dc}$

III. THE PROPOSED TECHNIQUE

The presented technique structure using ESMC is illustrated in Figure 3 with the transfer function of the first-order filter being:

$$F(p) = \frac{1}{T.p + 1} \quad (3)$$

where p is a derivative operator and T is the constant of time of the filter. Then, the phase voltage of load V_{r1x} is:

$$V_{r1x} = \frac{1}{T.p + 1} V_f \quad (4)$$

The phase voltage of load V_{r1x} is defined as:

$$V_{r1x} = R i_x + L \dot{i}_x \quad (5)$$

where the dot above the i_x serves as the derivative of current. Therefore, the output of SMC V_f is:

$$V_f = V_{r1x} + T\dot{V}_{r1x} = Ri_x + Li_x + T(R\dot{i}_x + L\ddot{i}_x) \quad (6)$$

The 2nd-order derivative of the current is:

$$\ddot{i}_x = \frac{V_f - (Li_x + Ri_x + TR\dot{i}_x)}{TL} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. Proposed control technique.

The difference between the reference value i_{refx} and the measured value of load current i_x , is the error e . The sliding surface S is chosen as:

$$S = \dot{e} + \alpha e \text{ with } \alpha > 0 \quad (8)$$

Then, we can deduce:

$$\dot{S} = \ddot{e} + \alpha \dot{e} = \ddot{i}_{refx} - \frac{[V_f - (Li_x + Ri_x + TR\dot{i}_x)]}{TL} + \alpha \dot{e} \quad (9)$$

The chosen control law is:

$$\dot{S} = -\beta \tanh\left(\frac{S}{\gamma}\right) - \mu S + \frac{Ri_x}{TL} + \dot{i}_{refx} \quad \gamma, \mu > 0 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{with } \beta > \left| \frac{Ri_x}{TL} + \dot{i}_{refx} \right|$$

Then:

$$V_f = TL \left[\beta \tanh\left(\frac{S}{\gamma}\right) + \mu S + \alpha \dot{e} \right] + (RT + L^2)\dot{i}_x \quad (11)$$

An RBF network is used to estimate the component N_e as follows:

$$N_e = (RT + L^2)\dot{i}_x \quad (12)$$

where:

$$\dot{i}_x = \dot{i}_{refx} - \dot{e} \quad (13)$$

The structure of this network has 2 inputs, e and the derivative of e , the hidden layer has 5 neural cells, and the output is N_e . The cells of the hidden layer are defined as:

$$g(x)_i = \exp\left(-\sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{\|x - c_i\|^2}{2\sigma^2}\right]\right) \quad (14)$$

Then, we can deduce:

$$\hat{N}_e = \hat{w}^T * g \quad (15)$$

Then:

$$V_f = TL \left[\beta \tanh\left(\frac{S}{\gamma}\right) + \mu S + \alpha \dot{e} \right] + \hat{N}_e \quad (16)$$

where g is the Gauss function, \hat{w} is an estimated weight matrix, and \hat{N}_e is the estimated output of the RBF network used as a component of the controller. Then, the output voltage of the proposed controller is described in (16), and the structure of the controller is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Structure of the controller using NN.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation system's parameters, along with the step changes in reference currents, are presented in Table II. There are 4 intervals of time, corresponding to 40 fundamental periods, each interval of 0.2 s with the reference peak current steps as 40 A, 30 A, 20 A, and 10 A respectively. The two method results are shown in Figures 5-12.

TABLE II. PARAMETERS OF THE SYSTEM

Description	Value
Voltage of the DC source	180 V
Angular frequency	100 π rad/s
Parameters of current controller K_p, K_i	0.1, 500
Load of each phase R and L	8.5 Ω and 5 mH
Frequency of carriers for POD f_c	3 kHz
Constant C	0.5
Constants $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \mu, T$	3; 0.05; 0.05; 3.75×10^5 ; 3.97×10^{-5}

The method employing POD-PR provides the reference voltages in Figure 5(a) based on the reference currents, while the presented technique using ESMC offers those in Figure 5(b). The reference phase voltages of the two methods are zoomed in 0.16-0.2 s in Figures 6(a)-(b). Voltage waveforms have a significant difference in the ripples. The ripples in Figure 6(b) change in levels ± 0.25 V and ± 0.75 V, leading to the results in Figures (7)-(10).

Fig. 5. Reference phase voltages: (a) POD-PR and (b) proposed method.

Fig. 6. Reference phase voltages zoomed in 0.16-0.2 s: (a) POD-PR and (b) proposed method.

Fig. 7. Waveforms of POD-PR: (a) phase voltages, (b) phase-phase voltage and CMV, and (c) phase currents.

Normally, for multilevel 3-phase inverters, the voltage output of the inverter has only 3 phase wires and no neutral wire. Therefore, the phase-phase voltage quality should be considered and evaluated. The waveforms in Figure 7(b) show that the phase-phase voltage magnitude is up to $4 \times V_{dc}$, as 720 V, in the three intervals from 0-0.6 s. This can also be clearly seen in Figure 9(b), while in Figure 8(b) of the proposed technique, it only exists in the first interval of 0-0.2 s. In the second and the third intervals, it is only $3 \times V_{dc}$ and $2 \times V_{dc}$, respectively. This can also be clearly seen in Figure 10(b).

The spectrum and THD value of the phase-phase voltage in Figure 11 are taken at the last period of every interval. The spectrum and THD value of the POD-PR method are illustrated in Figures 11(a)-(b), respective to the first interval and the last one. Similarly, those of the proposed technique are depicted in Figures 11(c)-(d). Those of the second and the third intervals also gave similar results. The THD values of the four intervals are summarized in Figure 12(a).

Fig. 8. Waveforms of ESMC: (a) phase voltages, (b) phase-phase voltage and CMV, and (c) phase currents.

Fig. 9. Waveforms of POD-PR zoomed in 0.18-0.28 s: (a) phase voltage, (b) phase-phase voltage and CMV, and (c) phase currents.

Fig. 10. Waveforms of the proposed technique zoomed in 0.18-0.28 s: (a) phase voltage, (b) phase-phase voltage and CMV, and (c) phase currents.

Although the phase-phase voltage of the POD-PR method has a level number greater than that of the proposed technique, its THD values are always higher than those of the technique suggested (Figures 11 and 12(a)). Its THD values are up to 26.88%, 40.29%, 65.03%, and 123.22%, respectively. On the other hand, those of the proposed technique are only 18.51%, 26.36%, 38.91%, and 80.95%, respectively.

Moreover, the highest individual harmonic magnitudes of the POD-PR method are up to 14% and 73%, respectively, in Figures 11(a)-(b) for the first (0-0.2 s) and the last interval (0.6-0.8 s), while those of the ESMC method are significantly low, only 4.84% and 23.3%, respectively (Figures 11(c)-(d)). This demonstrates the capability of the ESMC technique to distribute the spectrum across a broad range.

Fig. 11. Spectrum of phase-phase voltage: (a)-(b) POD-PR method and (c)-(d) proposed method.

Fig. 12. (a) THD of phase-phase voltage and (b) switching count of each fundamental period.

In the entire time surveyed, from 0-0.8 s, there are 40 fundamental periods. The switching counts of the two methods in each 0.02 s period are presented in Figure 12(b). These results show that the switching counts of the proposed technique (Figure 12(b)) are always smaller than those of the POD-PR method, thus reducing the switching loss of the inverter.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a method for controlling three-phase MLIs using an enhanced sliding mode control technique based on neural networks, aimed at reducing the common mode voltage magnitude as achieved by the POD modulation. Additionally, this technique aids in decreasing the switching counts and minimizing voltage harmonics of MLIs. The proposed approach eliminates the need for carrier signals for modulation and PR current controllers, thereby streamlining hardware computations. Simulation results substantiate the efficacy of this method in a cascaded 5-level, 3-phase inverter system when compared to the conventional approach employing carriers of POD modulation and PR current controllers. Furthermore, the method's ability to distribute the spectrum over a wide range significantly diminishes the amplitudes of highest individual harmonics. This can help inverter to not need to use the passive filter at the output while power quality is guaranteed. In addition, this also lowers the acoustic noise to telecommunication and military equipment. In future research, this technique will be applied to reduce the current harmonics and the switching counts of MLIs of the grid-connected systems.

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Performance Analysis of a New Vertical Axis Turbine Design for Household Usage

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ABSTRACT

The popularity of small wind turbines intended for domestic use has significantly increased during the recent years, and it is reasonable to assume that this trend will continue given the present political and economic environment. There is a greater need for clean, pollution-free energy due to worries about climate change. In this study, a 1.5 KW vertical-axis Darrieus helix wind turbine for residential use was designed and its performance was mathematically evaluated under typical wind speed circumstances of 12 m/s. The study is split into two sections: In the first, we examined a standard wind turbine design with three identical blades, whereas in the second, the blades were different, each with a unique airfoil with a varying chord, even though they shared the same rotor diameter. For each case, 5 CFD simulations were performed in order to determine the power characteristics of the wind turbines. To correctly set up the computational domain, the number of elements and the minimum element size were taken into account whereas mesh dependency analysis was performed. In order to compare the results, the vorticity magnitude was measured at 4 different blade locations in each boundary condition. The results showed that when the power coefficient of the turbines is considered, such geometry adjustments are possible. Furthermore, the evolution of the torque coefficient over a full 360-degree rotation was studied. A summary of the improvements in performance resulting from the geometry adjustment is provided.

Keywords-vertical-axis wind turbine; Darrieus; CFD; power coefficient

I. INTRODUCTION

The world's energy systems are radically changing to focus on environmentally friendly and sustainable options [1]. At the same time wind power is becoming a key component in this search for renewable energy. In the current context of energy crisis [2] and of a potential future crisis [3], European Union regulations on nullifying combustion gas emissions by the year 2050 make the development of alternative energy sources like wind turbines or solar power plants [4], one of the only viable options to sustain a society that depends on electricity [5]. Energy availability over the past 30 years [6] shows how difficult and slow it is to eliminate natural gas, solid fossil fuels, and petroleum product exploitation as energy sources. While renewable energy sources have steadily increased in quantity, burning-dependent energy sources have declined at a

much slower pace. The current longevity of wind turbines has only served to further slow down this process—after a mean service life of about 20 years, the blades need to be replaced, whereas the old parts are either recycled, burned, or end up in landfills. This raises a number of environmental concerns about these energy sources effects [7].

Wind energy, a promising and eco-friendly resource, has shown remarkable growth over the past few decades [8]. Notable examples that have made substantial contributions to wind energy expansion include countries such as Romania [9], Switzerland [10], or China [11, 12]. Furthermore, the European Union as a whole has experienced significant advancements in wind energy utilization [13, 14]. Due to their advantages over the Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs) [15], in urban and suburban locations [16], Vertical Axis Wind Turbines

(VAWTs) have become a feasible alternative among all wind turbine configurations for home usage. Owing to their omnidirectional operation, smaller and more space-efficient design, and quieter operation [17, 18] than those of an HAWT, the VAWTs are more suitable for domestic use. Wind turbines categorization does not solely take axis orientation into account. Wind turbines can be categorized by how the turbines interact with the electrical grid (off-grid or on-grid) and how they harvest the wind kinetic energy (with the help of the drag force or the lift force). However, the same mathematical formula [19] - which states that wind power is exactly proportional to speed to the third power - is used to begin the design process in all cases.

A wind turbine's operating environment [20], including its intended power output, average wind speed in the region, placement height, and terrain, must be taken under consideration during the designing process. It is essential to analyze the average wind speed [21] in the area. This analysis is important in determining the turbine primary dimensions (height and diameter) as well as the number of blades the turbine should use. Odd numbers of blades are advised since even numbers significantly reduce the tip speed ratio interval across which the turbine can produce power [22]. The latter also increase the possibility of aerodynamic equilibrium [23], which might leave the turbine ineffective in the starting process. Geometry adaptation is an essential way to improve VAWT performance. Researchers are investigating ways to optimize turbine height, support structures, blade positioning [24], blade shape [25], number of blades [26], and the number of rotors through iterative design modifications and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) - based analysis. Authors in [27] examine a new VAWT with two counter-rotating rotors. Furthermore, in order to achieve greater efficiency and lower cut-in speeds, variables like material choice, blade curvature, and aerodynamic characteristics are crucial. As a result, VAWTs are more suited for low-wind speed areas frequently encountered in urban environments [28].

The simulation of CFD models use has become an indispensable method in contemporary wind turbine design when it comes to maximizing the power coefficient and the overall efficiency while trying to minimize the cost. The complex fluid flow phenomena surrounding VAWTs, which are governed by the Navier-Stokes equations [29], may be thoroughly examined using CFD models. Genetic algorithms [30] are a class of optimization algorithms that may be used to optimize the VAWT design [31]. They are inspired by the principles of genetics and natural selection. The initial population of possible VAWT designs is randomly generated at the first stage, and each design is represented by a set of parameters [32]. Subsequently, an assessment function will be employed to assess the effectiveness of every design. Afterwards, the genetic processes of selection, crossover, and mutation are implemented, and a fitness function is utilized to measure the performance of each design. Following that, the population evolves over a number of generations [33]. The best design of the final population is chosen when the algorithm stops, either by obtaining an optimum design or when a stop condition such as the maximum generations number is reached [34].

This research proposes a novel, asymmetric profile consisting of 3 distinct NACA airfoils with varied chord lengths positioned on the same radius. This new design intends to enhance the VAWT's overall performance and aerodynamic efficiency, especially in low-wind speed areas that are common in urban environments. The suggested adaptation of the geometry has the potential to improve energy extraction while preserving the small size and space-saving design of VAWTs.

II. GEOMETRY GENERATION

This study examined two geometric cases: the first has 3 identical NACA airfoils with the same chord length that are symmetrically positioned with respect to the turbine vertical axis of symmetry. The second involves 3 distinct NACA airfoils with varying chord lengths. Five simulations were run for each example in order to determine the relationship between the power coefficient and the Tip Speed Ratio (TSR). A 3D CAD model of the VAWTs under consideration is displayed in Figure 2, along with a cross-section for each case.

Fig. 1. The Darrieus VAWT: (a) baseline, (b) new solution.

The parameters of both geometries taken into consideration are listed in Table I. The final value taken into account in the final results is the chord's second value. In order to enhance the performance of blades 1 and 3, which were determined to have a lower power coefficient than the second blade following a CFD simulation at the ideal TSR, the chord was increased.

TABLE I. GEOMETRY PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	
	Baseline case	New case
Blade 1 airfoil	NACA0020	NACA0012
Blade 2 airfoil		NACA0018
Blade 3 airfoil		NACA0024
Blade 1 chord	0.3 m	0.33 m
Blade 2 chord		0.3 m
Blade 3 chord		0.356 m
Blade diameter	2 m	2 m
Blade height	3 m	3 m
Wind speed	12 m/s	12 m/s

III. NUMERICAL SIMULATION

A three-dimensional simulation is perhaps the most accurate way to simulate the flow around a wind turbine. This research focuses on the airflow in a two-dimensional sector of the turbine, since the primary drawback of the 3-D simulation is the computational work and time required to complete the simulation. Nevertheless, this will not allow the consideration of the impact of the vortices that may be formed at the top or the bottom of each blade. The two-dimensional geometries under analysis were created using the Ansys Design Modeler and were then simulated with the Ansys Fluent. An interface was formed between the rotor and stator regions of the partitioned spatial domain. For mesh dependency analysis, three distinct meshes were created for the basis geometry, as indicated in Table II. The dimensions of the considered domain used in the CFD simulations are displayed in Figure 2.

TABLE II. BASELINE GEOMETRY MESHES

Mesh number	Type	Number of elements
1	Coarse	~150,000
2	Medium	~200,000
3	Fine	~250,000

Fig. 2. Dimensions of the domain: stator region with zoom on the rotor region, where D is the turbine diameter and c is the baseline blade chord.

The disposition of the fine mesh elements can be observed in Figure 3. The boundary conditions for each simulation were defined as indicated in Figure 4. The intake condition specifies the air inlet velocity, which is 12 m/s. The interface defines the connection between the rotor and the stator and allows the air to flow from one region to the other. The flow region area is defined internally. The exit pressure of the air is defined as 101325 Pa, the standard pressure at mean sea level. Symmetry is set between the two borders of the stator region (the highest and lowest frontiers), and Wall denotes the portion of the blades (the airfoil) that prevents air flow.

The SST $k-\omega$ model, which solves a set of two partial derivative differential equations for the turbulence kinetic energy (k) and the particular dissipation rate (ω) for each element on the mesh, is the turbulence model utilized in this study

Fig. 3. Mesh: (a) baseline, (b) new solution, (c) zoom on the blade's inflation.

Fig. 4. Boundary conditions in Ansys Fluent.

Five case studies were explored for each mesh type, each corresponding to a different TSR value between 1 and 3. The relation between the TSR and the rotational velocity (ω) is:

$$TSR = \frac{\omega D}{2V} \tag{1}$$

where V represents the wind speed and D is the turbine diameter. The rotational velocity and time step size, which represent one degree of angular movement during every iteration, are computed for every case by (1).

The primary goal of the CFD simulations is to capture the fluctuation in the torque coefficient with the turbine's azimuth angle (θ) throughout 10 complete rotor revolutions. This information is then used to compute the mean value of the torque coefficient during the last rotation:

$$\overline{C_m} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{360} C_{m,i} \Delta t}{\sum_{i=1}^{360} \Delta t} \tag{2}$$

Equation (3) is used to calculate the power coefficient (C_p) of the wind turbine based on the mean value of its torque coefficient:

$$C_p = TSR \cdot \overline{C_m} \tag{3}$$

IV. RESULTS

Following the simulations completion, the torque coefficient (C_m) in the first scenario could be shown to repeat itself during a full rotation. At 120 degrees of azimuth angle θ the variation's maxima and minima are equally spaced, suggesting that the geometry is made up of 3 identical blades. After the mesh dependency study, where nominal TSR value was used, we conducted the remaining simulation with the medium mesh size. The torque coefficient quantifies the effectiveness of a wind turbine in converting wind energy's kinetic energy into mechanical torque, which can subsequently produce electricity. The ratio between the actual mechanical torque generated by the wind turbine rotor and the greatest theoretical torque that might be generated with the same wind speed and rotor area is known as the torque coefficient. Figure 6 illustrates the variation of the torque coefficient of each blade.

Fig. 5. Torque coefficient variation for mesh dependency.

Fig. 6. Variation of torque coefficient, TSR = 2.5: (a) baseline, (b) proposed.

Visualizing the vorticity magnitude in CFD simulations is a useful method for understanding and depicting flow characteristics, such as the presence of swirl, rotational motion, and vortices in fluid flows. High vorticity magnitude indicates strong vortices, whereas low vorticity suggests more uniform or irrotational flow. For each case, the vorticity of the speed (velocity curl) shows the region where vertices are prone to form in the rotor region. Vorticity magnitude contours for both cases are displayed in Figure 7 at the nominal position when TSR is 2.5. Power coefficient is an important indicator in the wind energy sector because it helps measure how well a wind turbine converts wind energy into usable electricity. One of the main objectives in designing more environmentally friendly and economically competitive wind energy systems is to use VAWTs with greater C_p values. C_p is applied in CFD simulations to evaluate a VAWT design's performance at different wind speeds. A VAWT's operation and design may be optimized to improve energy extraction and efficiency by examining how C_p varies with wind speed and condition. Upon exploring the new geometry, it is possible to see that the change in the total power coefficient indicates an improvement over the base geometry brought in by the high TSR area.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The growing demand for energy can heavily diminish power availability, and considering the objective to completely eliminate burning fuels as an energy source, the only viable means of generating electricity are renewable energy sources. So, wind turbines emerge as a feasible alternative to tackle climate change and develop a sustainable energy grid which justifies why VAWTs (Darrieus-type) are becoming increasingly popular.

Fig. 7. Vorticity magnitude (a) baseline at $\theta = 0^\circ$, (a') new geometry at $\theta = 0^\circ$, (b) baseline at $\theta = 30^\circ$, (b') new geometry at $\theta = 30^\circ$, (c) baseline at $\theta = 60^\circ$, (c') new geometry at $\theta = 60^\circ$, (d) baseline at $\theta = 90^\circ$, (d') new geometry at $\theta = 90^\circ$.

Unsteady Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) studies are successfully completed in this paper for the comparison of two vertical axis wind turbine layouts under wind conditions of 12 m/s using the CFD software ANSYS Fluent. Each turbine has 3 blades positioned at the same radius, with the exception of the second turbine, which has a distinct airfoil shape for each blade. All simulations were performed in 2D, with 6 TSRs ranging from 1 to 3. As a consequence, for every numerically examined example, the entire torque coefficient values for full 360 degrees circle are displayed. The vorticity magnitude distribution for each wind turbine design was predicted by the simulations.

Furthermore, the new geometry analyzed in this paper has a better overall performance in high TSR regions than the base geometry. The former reaches higher values of torque coefficient and power coefficient, and results in a higher power output for the same wind conditions as the base geometry turbine. The wind kinetic energy resources found in the urban areas, along with the small sizes of these devices and their silent operation make these wind turbines a very attractive choice for any household user. This is because they lead to a certain degree of power independence and contribute to the reduction of the greenhouse gases emissions.

Fig. 8. C_p variation.

By using a new turbine profile with varied chord lengths and airfoils like the geometry studied in this paper, the performance of future generations of small urban-sized VAWTs will augment and make Darrieus-type VAWTs an even more attractive solution. In the future, an optimization with genetic algorithms will be performed in order to design a small prototype that can be tested under real-life settings in an experimental testing facility near the Black Sea where the wind speed is suitable for wind turbines.

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machines, mainly focusing on improving their performance. He has published over 50 scientific articles in both conferences and specialized journals. From 2009 he has been involved in over 30 national and international research projects. He reviews around 20 papers per year.

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Modeling and Simulation of a Renewable Energy PV/PEM with Green Hydrogen Storage

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of green hydrogen-based energy storage in association with renewable energy constitutes a promising and sustainable solution to the increase in energy demand while reducing greenhouse gas emissions. However, these hybrid systems face technical, economic, and logistic challenges that require a new transport and distribution architecture. The technical-economic study of these expensive installations requires good modeling and optimal sizing of the system components. This study presents a global model for hydrogen production and storage stations using photovoltaics (PV) and integrating Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) modules for electric vehicles. The simulations and sizing were based on the implementation of an effective mathematical model capable of accurately simulating the real dynamic behavior of the installation, the electrical and energy yields, the power consumed and produced, and finally the mass of hydrogen stored and/or consumed by the fuel cell. In this model, the hybrid system integrates PV solar panels with a maximum power of 1.2 MW, followed by a 1.0 MW Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzer, a high-pressure hydrogen storage tank, and a PEMFC to convert hydrogen into electricity. The simulation results showed that the energy generated by the PV panels can produce around 200 kg/day of green hydrogen by electrolysis, which makes it possible to power 100 electric cars per day with a range of 250 km for each.

Keywords- PV renewable energy; green hydrogen storage; fuel cell; PEM electrolyzer; energy efficiency; electrolysis

I. INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, unprecedented energy challenges, such as reducing emissions, diversifying energy sources, and meeting the growing demand, highlight the importance of sustainable energy production systems. Solar photovoltaics (PV) and hydrogen, as cutting-edge technologies, are key pillars in the transition to a cleaner and more sustainable energy future. Many studies have investigated challenges and promising solutions in solar PV green energy and hydrogen production, highlighting the intermittent nature of PV power and the need for energy storage systems to minimize fluctuations. Some studies have identified current gaps and provide recommendations for more accurate and informative

modeling to help analysts and policymakers improve the integration of renewable energy [1]. The aim is to ensure continuous and reliable hydrogen production. Many studies have focused on the modeling and simulation of such complex systems. This study aims to model and simulate a Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzer connected to a solar cell to better understand the factors affecting the production of hydrogen and oxygen. The difficulties include a precise model, temperature effects, and comparison with membrane-less electrolyzers. The results showed that PEM is suitable for hot, temperature-dependent desert regions and that an electrolyzer with a membrane produces much more hydrogen (2.25 l) than an electrolyzer without (0.0001 l) [2]. Hydrogen is considered a

promising energy source, but it faces challenges such as dependence on fossil fuels, high production costs, and storage problems [3].

To meet these challenges, the development of cost-effective hydrogen production technologies, notably through renewable energy and improved supply chain efficiency, aims to make hydrogen a viable, sustainable, and economically efficient energy source. One approach to producing green hydrogen is to combine electrolysis with chemical methods, using materials such as perovskites to improve the electrolyzer performance. Using solar energy as a primary energy source can reduce hydrogen production costs by up to 7% compared to high-temperature electrolysis [4]. Hydrogen energy can be used in fuel cells of vehicles, but choosing between compressed hydrogen gas and liquid hydrogen for refueling requires energy considerations, with liquid hydrogen potentially consuming more [5]. The efficient integration of energy sources such as PV modules, fuel cells, and electrolyzers can help solve energy storage problems. By using solar energy to produce hydrogen through electrolysis, it is possible to stabilize and ensure a continuous energy supply [6]. Another example of an innovative solution involves optimizing the scale of a hybrid system integrating solar panels, fuel cells, and hydrogen storage to meet the energy needs of laboratories. Such a system can provide stable power with 96.7% renewable energy at a comparative cost, resulting in significant energy savings and a rapid return on investment [7]. Furthermore, the development of hybrid solar PV and hydrogen systems in grid-connected buildings improves renewable energy utilization, achieving high green energy supply levels and reducing CO₂ emissions through energy sector decarbonization [8]. The development of energy management and capacity sizing models for hybrid solar PV and hydrogen systems in grid-connected buildings represents a significant step forward. In [9], the obtained results showed that a 4.31 MW PV system combined with a 2.28 MW electrolyzer, a 500 KW fuel cell, and a 1.331 Kg hydrogen tank can supply most of the building's energy while reducing electricity imports from the grid equivalent to a reduction of 612,005.76 Kg CO₂ per year. When creating accurate models for hybrid renewable energy in grid-connected buildings, the solution lies in precise component dimensions and realistic system simulations. A study carried out in a building of a European university demonstrated that the model can accurately simulate a hybrid system, increasing solar energy consumption and reducing CO₂ emissions [10]. Complex simulations and modeling were used to evaluate the performance and efficiency of such systems, validating their feasibility and usefulness in real-world applications [11-17]. These innovative approaches are necessary to meet the challenges of hydrogen as an energy carrier and contribute to the transition to cleaner and more sustainable energy.

II. MODELING GREEN STORAGE HYDROGEN

A. Global Storage Architecture of Green Hydrogen

Solar hydrogen production and storage systems use solar energy to generate hydrogen by electrolysis, which is stored for later use. The system consists of several basic components, as shown in Figure 1. At first, 1.2 MW photovoltaic solar panels harness the energy of the sun to generate electricity. This

electricity is then fed into a 1 MW PEM electrolyzer, which splits water into hydrogen and oxygen using the electricity generated by solar panels. The hydrogen produced is then stored in a specially designed high-pressure storage tank. The system contributes to the transition to clean, renewable energy by providing a sustainable energy storage solution that produces hydrogen from solar energy.

Fig. 1. Storage architecture of the green hydrogen system.

B. Modeling of the Green Hydrogen System

The modeling and simulation process of the system comprises various components, such as PV panels, DC converters, hydrogen PEM electrolyzer, hydrogen storage tanks, and a PEM fuel cell, which are interconnected to construct the system model, as shown in Figure 2. The simulation was carried out using MATLAB, considering solar irradiation and ambient temperature. The mathematical models that represent the various components of the system were simulated using Simulink blocks, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Simulink model of the hydrogen production and storage system.

C. Modeling of the PV Generator Equations

Mathematical models were used to evaluate the energy efficiency of PV cells, optimize the solar energy system, and evaluate its environmental impact. The output voltage of a PV cell is determined by the photocurrent, which is mainly influenced by the load current and the level of solar radiation during operation, as stated in [6, 17-21].

$$I_{PV} = N_p I_L - N_p I_S \left[\exp \left(\frac{q \left(\frac{V_{PV} + I_{RS}}{N_s} \right)}{nkT} \right) - 1 \right] - \frac{N_s V_{PV}}{R_{sh}} \quad (1)$$

where I_0 is the PV cell reverse saturation current (A), I_{PV} is the PV cell output current (A), I_{sc} is the short-circuit cell current (A), k is the Boltzmann's constant [j/K], N_p is the number of parallel strings ($N_p=78$), N_s is the number of series cells per string ($N_s =39$), q is the electron charge (C), R_s is the series resistance of the PV cell (Ω), T is the PV cell temperature (K), and V_{PV} is the terminal voltage for the PV cell (V). The PV model available in the MATLAB software library was used and its parameters were adjusted to the specific needs of this study.

D. Modeling of the Converter

DC-DC converters offer significant flexibility and high efficiency in controlling power in DC circuits. In the examined solar green hydrogen production system, a back-boost converter was used in combination with MPPT and P&O control. In this way, the PV system optimizes the production of solar energy to power the electrolyzer for hydrogen production, thereby contributing to the efficient and sustainable use of renewable energy. This system can also track the maximum power point under different irradiation and temperature conditions. The system of equations for a buck-boost converter in steady-state operation is provided in [22-23]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{dL}{dt} \\ \frac{dV_S}{dt} \\ \frac{dI_S}{dt} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{1-d}{L} & 0 \\ -\frac{1-d}{c} & 0 & -\frac{1}{c} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} I_L \\ V_S \\ I_S \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{d}{L} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where V_{PV} and V_S are the input and output voltages, c is the capacitance of the dc-bus, L is the value of the inductance, and D represents the control signal of the switches.

E. Modeling the Hydrogen PEM Electrolyzer

The Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzer is considered a viable alternative for hydrogen production from Renewable Energy Sources (RES). Many PEM fuel cell models have been reported, but few PEM electrolyzer models [17, 24-25]. Recently, the modeling of PEM electrolyzers has attracted growing interest from industry and researchers to optimize, design, and appropriately use PEM electrolyzers. The parameters used to model the electrolyzer are: I_{el} and V_{El} is the current and the voltage of the electrolyzer (A, V), respectively, P_{El} is the power (KW), and η_F is the Faraday efficiency [26]:

$$\eta_F = 96.5e^{\left(\frac{0.09}{I_{El}} - \frac{75.5}{I_{El}^2}\right)} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{El}(t) = V_{in} + V_{anode}(t) + V_{cathode}(t) + R_{el}(t)I_{El}(t) \quad (4)$$

$$I_{El}(t) = I_{anode1}(t) + I_{anode2}(t)$$

$$= I_{cathode1}(t) + I_{cathode2}(t) \quad (5)$$

$$P_{El}(t) = I_{El}(t) \times V_{El}(t) \quad (6)$$

V_{El} is the voltage of the PEM electrolyzer, and V_{in} , $V_{anode}(t)$, $V_{cathode}(t)$, $R_{el}(t)$, $I_{El}(t)$, $I_{anode1}(t)$, $I_{anode2}(t)$, $I_{cathode1}(t)$, $I_{cathode2}(t)$, are, respectively, the open circuit voltage, the voltage losses in the anodes and cathodes, the electrolytes ohmic resistance, the stack current, the currents in the resistive and capacitive anode branches, and the currents in the resistive and capacitive cathode branches. Modeling the hydrogen production from the electrolyzer using RES is needed to account for changes resulting from load variations. Large electrolyzers are made up of cells connected in series. An integrated power unit controls current density and gas generation. Standard voltages for large electrolyzer installations are typically 400 V, 600 V, or 11 KV, depending on the size. Faraday efficiency is used to accurately quantify the hydrogen production of an electrolyzer, taking into account current losses due to gas diffusion. These losses affect the hydrogen production rate and vary with current. This is crucial, as the hourly variation in faraday efficiency is linked to the amount of hydrogen produced. The total hydrogen produced by an electrolyzer consisting of multiple stacks can be accordingly identified based on the number of operational stacks based on the law of ideal gases:

$$V_{H2}(t) = \eta_F(t) \frac{n_e I_{El}(t)}{2F} \quad (7)$$

The quantity of hydrogen produced by an electrolyzer consisting of several cells can be determined correspondingly by the operating number of cells, as shown in (8).

$$m_{H2prod}(t) = V_{H2} \times M \times n_c(t) \times 3600 \quad (8)$$

where n_c is the number of cells within the electrolyzer, I_{el} is the current applied to a single cell of the electrolyzer, the Faraday constant F is 96485.33 C/mol, T is the operating temperature of the electrolyzer (K), $m_{H2prod}(t)$ is the hourly mass of total hydrogen production by the electrolyzer unit (kg/h), $\eta_F(t)$ is the Faraday efficiency at the value of current absorbed by the electrolytic cell, and M is the molar mass of the hydrogen gas (2.016×10^{-3} kg/mol). The model of the PEM electrolyzer was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Simulink model of the PEM electrolyzer.

F. Modeling of the Hydrogen Storage Tank

The modeling of a hydrogen storage tank is essential for evaluating the performance of a hydrogen storage system. Gas equations of state, such as the ideal gas equation or the Van der Waals equation, are used to accurately simulate the behavior of the hydrogen inside the tank. The flow rate of the hydrogen is calculated at the operating pressure by:

$$P = z \frac{m_{H_2} R T_{tank}}{M V T_{tank}} + P_{initial} \tag{9}$$

where P is the gas pressure in pascals (Pa), m_{H_2} is the mass quantity of hydrogen, R is the gas constant equal to 8.314 J/K·mol, T_{tank} is the absolute temperature of the gas (K), V_{tank} is the gas volume (m³), and z is the compressibility factor [17, 27]. The size of the hydrogen storage tank is determined by the amount of hydrogen consumed by the fuel cell. The system uses a hydrogen-based fuel that is charged during sunny hours and discharged at night to meet needs. The mass of hydrogen available in the storage tank at the time step in question is:

$$m_{tank}(t) = m_{init} + \int (H_{2in} - dm_{out}) (t) \tag{10}$$

where $m_{tank}(t)$ is the hydrogen mass available in the storage tank at time step t (kg/h), $m_{init}(t)$ is the hydrogen storage tank hourly mass status, H_{2in} is the mass of hydrogen product (kg/h), dm_{out} is the mass of hydrogen consumed by the fuel cells. The hydrogen storage tank is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Simulink model of the hydrogen storage tank.

G. Modeling of the PEM Fuel Cell

In the PEM fuel cell, a solid polymer membrane is used as the electrolyte, allowing electrons to move around while limiting protons. This forces electrons to travel outside the membrane, generating an electric current that can be used later. The PEM fuel cell is known for its high energy efficiency, minimal pollutant emissions, reduced dependence on fossil fuels, and low greenhouse gas emissions. The flow rate hydrogen consumption by a stack PEM fuel cell is given by:

$$dm_{out}(t) = \frac{P_{FC}(t)}{PCI * \eta_{FC}} \tag{11}$$

where $dm(t)$ is the hydrogen mass consumption of the fuel cell (kg/h), P_{fc} is the power of the PEM fuel cell system, PCI is the lower hydrogen calorific value, and η_{fc} is the efficiency of the fuel cell. The fuel cell was simulated in MATLAB/Simulink as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Simulink model of the fuel cell.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The green hydrogen production and storage system uses PV solar energy to produce hydrogen through water electrolysis. The hydrogen produced is stored in a tank for later use [28]. This system offers a long-term renewable energy storage solution that can be used when solar energy is not available, such as during nighttime or cloudy days.

A. Characteristics of the PV Panel

The green hydrogen production and storage system includes a 1.2 MW PV capacity in conjunction with a 1MW PEM electrolyzer unit, a 500 KW PEM fuel cell system, and a 350 Kg pressurized hydrogen storage tank, as illustrated in Table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED PV SYSTEM

Parameters	Value/type
Total PV installed capacity	1200 kW
Total number of PV modules	3042
Total Area requirement	7.560 km ²
PV Modules connection	78 strings×39 in series
nominal power of each PV Module	400 W
short-circuit current (I_{sc})	7.66 A
Open-circuit voltage (V_{oc})	48.5 V

TABLE II. COMPONENTS OF THE HYDROGEN SYSTEM

Components	PV Solar	Electrolyser	Storage tank	PEMFC
Capacity	1.2 MW	1MW	800Kg	500KW

B. Simulation Results

Simulations were carried out using MATLAB/Simulink, integrating real data from June 2020, including solar irradiation and ambient temperature. Tables I and II show the parameters used to develop the models for the PEM electrolyzer, hydrogen storage, and PEM fuel cell system, which were inspired from [9]. Figure 6 represents the daily load power request, and Figures 7 and 8 illustrate the ambient temperature and PV power outputs. Figures 8 and 9 show the hourly hydrogen production rate by the PEM electrolyzer. It can be concluded that the selected electrolyzer operates at variable power levels in response to intermittent solar energy generation to store excess PV energy in the form of green hydrogen during hours of excess solar energy production and the mass of hydrogen consumed by the fuel cell. Figure 10 shows the hourly mass of hydrogen stored, with a maximum value of up to 250 Kg. Figure 11 represents the simulation results of H₂ production as a function of electrical current. As the current supply to the electrolyzer increases, the bond-breaking dissociation reaction of the water molecules increases rapidly. The simulation results were compared with those of [29].

Fig. 6. Load demand (kW).

Fig. 7. Hourly ambient temperature.

Fig. 8. Hourly PV power generation.

Fig. 9. The mass flow rate of hydrogen production and the mass of hydrogen consumed by the fuel cell (dm_{out}).

Fig. 10. The stored hydrogen masses.

Fig. 11. H_2 production as a function of current.

C. Discussion

To evaluate the performance of the developed model in terms of real-world production, the simulation results shown in

Figures 7 to 12 were compared with those of [10], considering the electrochemical losses occurring in the PEM electrolyzer and the PEM fuel cells. According to the simulations of the hydrogen levels in the hydrogen tank, the maximum level reached in the hydrogen tank was 250 kg of hydrogen with the proposed model, compared to approximately 86.5 kg in [10]. This highlights the potential benefits of the proposed model for more accurately determining the capacity of hydrogen storage systems, thus avoiding the possibility of oversizing associated with additional costs and space requirements. Furthermore, it confirms that the accumulated hydrogen volume never exceeds the maximum recommended storage capacity of the hydrogen tank. The corresponding operating pressure achieved at this time was around 350 bar, confirming the recommended pressure for the hydrogen tank.

IV. CONCLUSION

Green hydrogen production and storage systems constitute a very viable option to meet the needs of various areas (industries, transport, storage, buildings, etc.) and contribute to an economy with low greenhouse gas emissions. In this context, this study developed a global model of a hydrogen production and storage station using PVs and integrating a PAC module to power electric vehicles for sustainable development and the protection of the ecosystem. A mathematical model was developed to evaluate the station's performance and optimize its operation and production. Storage efficiency and volume increased by approximately 30% under real climate conditions and dynamic PV behavior. This is very important to support sustainable transport and the green industry in the context of renewable energy integration, ensuring a sustainable energy transition.

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A Deep Learning Model to Inspect Image Forgery on SURF Keypoints of SLIC Segmented Regions

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ABSTRACT

Copy-Move Forgery (CMF) is a common form of image manipulation attack that involves copying and pasting a part of an image to another position within the same image. This study proposes a Deep Learning (DL) model for detecting CMF, particularly in the presence of various malicious attacks. The proposed approach involves several steps, including converting the input image to grayscale, preprocessing the image using the Simple Linear Iterative Clustering (SLIC) algorithm to generate superpixel partitions, and then extracting keypoint features using the Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF) detector. Finally, a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) is employed for feature description and matching. To assess the effectiveness of the approach, the types of features used for copy-move forgery were addressed. The proposed approach was examined under rotation, blurring, jpg compression, and scaling attacks. Furthermore, experimental results showed that the proposed approach can detect multiple CMFs with high accuracy. Finally, the proposed method was compared with recent state-of-the-art methods.

Keywords-image forgery; SURF keypoints; deep learning; SLIC segmentation

I. INTRODUCTION

Every user can share and exchange multimedia through social media networks. Multimedia content is exposed to several violations, therefore, the concept of multimedia security includes several ways of protection [1]. The increasing spread of ways to create and modify images, due to the presence of many available relative tools and software, has led to an increase in manipulated images, which can spread deceptive information [2]. Fake news uses multimedia content to mislead people based on fake visual content. Fake news often relies on sensitive or even incorrect images to elicit outrage or other emotional responses from consumers to encourage their spread. For this reason, it is necessary to verify the authenticity of these images, since the images express a lot of major information in many areas such as the field of criminal investigation, insurance dealing, financial reports, intelligent processing, journalism, and medical imaging. It is also critical to detect them because the process of unauthorized image manipulation affects the reading of images and changes the results associated with them. In light of this, many researchers are trying to develop algorithms to detect image forgery [3]. CMF is one of the most prominent image manipulations, as shown in Figure 1.

Digital image forgery is classified into active [4-5] and passive [6] approaches. The active approach means that when an image is created, some information is included within it to achieve the principle of attributing the image to its owner.

When processing the image and trying to extract this information, it becomes clear whether the image has been modified or not. The lack of this information when trying to extract it means that the image has been modified. The passive approach is a blind approach to detect if the image has been tampered with or not, based on the characteristics and some features in the image itself without a referenced image. Regarding the passive approach, the image forgeri methods are [7]:

- Copy-move forgery: falsifying images by copying a portion of the image and moving it to another place [8].
- Image splicing: inserting a piece of one or more imported images into the original to deceive the viewer [9]. This is a very common image forgery manipulation.
- Image retouching: applying some enhancement or filtering to an image [10].
- Image resampling: change of geometrical properties in some content of the image, such as rotation, flipping, reflection, expansion, and skewness [11].
- Image morphing: forming a new image that is completely different from two previous images. The necessary effects are made to harmonize the two images with each other [12].

CMF is one of the most important algorithms for detecting image forgery, concerned with finding copies of a portion in

the image and moving it to another place within the same image. The task of coping part of the image and then pasting it to another place is trivial and can be found with the naked eye, but many transformations can be also applied, such as scaling, blurring, etc., to delude the spectator of the image that it is a real image without any manipulation. Figure 2 shows the general approach to the CMF process for the copied region P1 and the moved region P2 in the image itself with translation, rotation, or scaling attacks, respectively.

Fig. 1. Classification of security attacks in image forgery detection methods.

Fig. 2. CMF mechanism.

The main problem is image violation through copy-move forgery by trying to copy an object or hide something in the image. To solve this issue, a DL model was used to detect copy-move forgeries by investigating keypoints in segmented regions. The main objectives of this study were: (1) To accurately determine copy-move forgery regarding malicious attacks, (2) To detect objects or regions regarding primitive features using SURF, (3) To develop a robust detection algorithm against various transformations, such as rotation, scaling, and various jpeg compression factors. The proposed model combines two algorithms, SLIC segmentation and SURF feature extraction, to achieve both accurate localization of the forged regions and effective feature extraction for accurate detection of copy-move forgeries. Some advantages of using SLIC and SURF together are:

- Computational efficiency: The SLIC algorithm can efficiently reduce the number of pixels in a single image, making it easier to compute feature descriptors faster using the SURF algorithm. This helps to minimize the

computational complexity and processing time of digital image analysis and processing tasks.

- Robustness: The SURF algorithm [13] was designed to be robust to various image transformations, such as scaling, rotation, and affine distortion.

II. RELATED WORKS

CMFD methods are classified into three categories [14-15]:

- Keypoint-based [16] identifies and chooses regions with high entropy in the image. The process of selecting keypoints starts from the preprocessing step that converts the image to grayscale to facilitate the extraction of primitive features of regions of interest in the image using the local maxima algorithm. Due to the power of the keypoint algorithm in detecting primitive features for any region manipulated with many geometric transformations, such as rotation, resizing, occlusion, and noise, it is widely applied to find the origin of images and recognize objects.
- Block-based [17]: Image regions are divided as overlapping square or circular blocks, and then the feature vector is calculated to characterize a strong and low-dimensional representation of the characteristics of the local image. Then, blocks of similar characteristics are matched according to the extracted descriptors. There is often a Euclidean distance between the descriptors to evaluate the similarity between two blocks.
- Segmentation-based [18-19]: Such methods suggest preprocessing the suspected image by dividing it into semantically independent regions through a segmentation algorithm, where the comparison between them is performed to increase the accuracy of matching similar regions.

Some studies used DL-based methods in the field of CMFD [20]. In [21], the mask region-based convolution neural network was proposed, which is a DL approach to locate and segment modified portions of suspicious images. This method achieved an average precision of 0.769, however, it was insufficient to deal with postprocessing attacks because of its low representation of features' capacity. In [22], a customized CNN based on the VGG-16 model was proposed that used transfer learning to increase CMFD accuracy, but it was computationally expensive and took a long time to derive results. The training time was 2.8 hr while the inference time of an image was 0.0532 s. In [23], deep features, such as deep convolution neural networks, were used to perform boundary-to-pixel direction segmentation using the SD-Net method, although it is vulnerable to noise attacks.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Figure 3 shows the framework of the proposed CMFD. It consists of several processes, beginning with grayscale conversion of the suspicious image and preprocessing it into a collection of superpixels using SLIC segmentation. Then, it extracts the SURF features from each segment and matches them. Finally, GAN is used to filter out the real image. The proposed method aims to accurately detect copy-move forgery.

Fig. 3. Framework of the proposed CMFD.

A. Preprocessing Stage using SLIC Segmentation

Simple Linear Iterative Clustering (SLIC) is a method used to generate superpixels in an image. Superpixels are defined as groups of intensities that share common features, such as color palettes. The goal of SLIC segmentation is to divide an image into multiple regions with similar superpixels, making it more significant and easier to investigate. SLIC has various practical applications, including object detection and recognition tasks [24]. The SLIC algorithm works by merging pixels based on similar features such as colors. It operates in a five-dimensional color and image plane space, where the combined color and spatial information is used to effectively produce condensed and almost homogeneous superpixels. The algorithm is simple to use, with a lone parameter specifying the intended number of superpixels. Its performance in producing superpixels at a reduced computational cost has been demonstrated to be equivalent to or higher in quality than currently available state-of-the-art methods. Here is how the SLIC segmentation algorithm works:

1. Initialization: The algorithm starts by evenly distributing a set of cluster centers throughout the image plane. The number of cluster centers is determined by the desired number of superpixels.
2. Assignment: Each pixel is then assigned to the nearest cluster center based on its color palettes and spatial closure. The color similarity is measured in a 5-dimensional space, which combines the pixel's color information and its spatial location in the image.
3. Update: After the initial assignment, the cluster centers are updated by taking the mean color and position of all the pixels assigned to them.
4. Convergence: Steps 2 and 3 are repeated until the cluster centers no longer move significantly or a maximum number of iterations is reached. This ensures that the algorithm converges to a stable solution.
5. Postprocessing: Once the algorithm has converged, the final superpixel segmentation is obtained by labeling each pixel with the index of its corresponding cluster center.

The advantages of using the SLIC algorithm for image segmentation are:

- Speed: SLIC is a fast algorithm that can efficiently process large colored images, making it suitable for real-time applications and preprocessing tasks.

- Boundary adherence: SLIC has good boundary adherence, which means that the generated superpixels are closely aligned with the edges and contours of objects in the image.

This can be beneficial for the copy-move forgery detection task that requires accurate object localization and boundary detection. SLIC algorithm, as k-means [25], takes an intended number of regions K as input. The approximate size of each region in an image with N pixels is N/K pixels. Every grid interval $S = \sqrt{N/K}$ would have a region center C for approximately equal-sized regions. The region center C_k is represented as a five-dimensional vector $[R_k, G_k, B_k, x_k, y_k]$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$.

The first phase involves routinely sampling K region centers C_k on the image plane (x, y) at RGB channels R_k, G_k, B_k and moving them to the places corresponding to the lowest gradient position in a 3×3 neighborhood computed by:

$$G(x, y) = ||I(x + 1, y) - I(x - 1, y)||^2 + ||I(x, y + 1) - I(x, y - 1)||^2 \quad (1)$$

where $I(x, y)$ is the image corresponding to pixel x, y and $||\cdot||$ is the L_2 norm. This is done to avoid setting the center on an edge and to decrease the possibility of selecting a noisy pixel. Following that, each picture pixel is given to one of the segments based on distance, i.e. the distance between a pixel i and all the region centers is computed, and the pixel is assigned to the segment whose center has the shortest distance to i . The SLIC algorithm assumes that pixels associated with a region are located on the x, y plane inside a $2S \times 2S$ radius around the region's center. This step narrows the search area. The distance measure D is defined as the sum of the color space d_{RGB} and spatial space $d_{x,y}$ distances normalized by the grid interval S .

$$d_{RGB} = \sqrt{(R_k - R_i)^2 + (G_k - G_i)^2 + (B_k - B_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$d_{x,y} = \sqrt{(x_k - x_i)^2 + (y_k - y_i)^2} \quad (3)$$

$$D_s = d_{RGB} + \frac{m}{S} * d_{xy} \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the color and spatial distances in (4) are balanced using the variable $m = 10$. A higher number of superpixels will result in smaller superpixels and a more detailed segmentation, while a lower number of superpixels will result in larger superpixels and a more coarse segmentation, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Segmentation in low and high superpixel factors: (a) Original image, (b) low superpixel factor, and (c) high superpixel factor.

The output of the SLIC segmentation stage is a set of labeled subregions S_b in image I and the center c_i of each S_b in the i -th region are saved in feature $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_i]$, where i is the total number of segmented regions and depends on the pixel factor parameter.

The compactness factor controls the trade-off between the spatial distance and the color distance when assigning pixels to superpixels. As shown in Figure 5, from left to right, a lower compactness factor results in superpixels with more irregular subregions, while a larger compactness factor will result in superpixels with regular subregions, making it easier to locate the center of each subregion.

Fig. 5. SLIC segmentation in variant compactness factor: (a) Image, (b) compactness factor = 20, and (c) compactness factor = 60.

B. Keypoints Detection using SURF

Speeded-Up Robust Features (SURF) [13] detects and describes features in an image plane and is widely used in the field of computer vision applications, such as object recognition, image registration, and classification. It is an upgraded version of the SIFT algorithm [26] with improved speed. The algorithm produces 64 or 128 features by working in 4 steps: (1) Scale-space extrema detection, (2) keypoint localization, (3) orientation assignment, and (4) keypoint descriptor. The SURF algorithm has two parts, the detector and the descriptor. In the detector part, a Hessian matrix is used because of its detection performance strength, since it does not consume a lot of power for computation and produces accurate results. Given a point $p = (x, y)$ in an image I , the Hessian matrix $H(p, \sigma)$ at the point p and scale σ is defined as:

$$H(p, \sigma) = \begin{bmatrix} L_{xx}(p, \sigma) & L_{xy}(p, \sigma) \\ L_{yx}(p, \sigma) & L_{yy}(p, \sigma) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where $L_{xx}(p, \sigma)$, $L_{xy}(p, \sigma)$, $L_{yx}(p, \sigma)$, and $L_{yy}(p, \sigma)$ are the second-order Gaussian derivatives of image I at point p and scale σ . SURF additionally selects the scale using the Hessian determinant. The prevailing orientation is estimated by adding all responses within a 60° sliding orientation frame. The Laplacian is replaced by the Difference of Gaussian (DoG) to reduce the cost of computation. The image is then converted to an integral image to improve the speed of executing the box filter. For the descriptor part, SURF uses wavelet response, since it is invariant to lighting variables. The feature descriptor is based on the sum of the Haar wavelet response around the point of interest. A $20s \times 20s$ neighborhood is drawn around the keypoint, where s is the size, and it is divided into four quadrants. Horizontal and vertical wavelet responses are obtained for each subregion, and a vector is constructed as:

$$v = (\sum dx, \sum dy, \sum |dx|, \sum |dy|) \quad (6)$$

The wavelet response can be easily determined using an integral image at any scale σ , and is also invariant to the scale variable by converting the descriptor into a unit vector. Figures 6 and 7 show how features are extracted using the SURF algorithm and identify similar regions in the image itself. The result of this stage is to determine the keypoints of the segmented regions S_b that start from the center c_i of each S_b .

Fig. 6. Detection of SURF keypoint features.

Fig. 7. Locate similar keypoints and matching between image regions.

C. Deep Learning Model using GAN

The Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) [27] is one of the most significant recent advancements in the field of unsupervised deep generative models. Figure 8 depicts the architecture of a typical GAN, which consists of two main neural networks motivated by the two-player min-max game: a generator and a discriminator. The generator attempts to create genuine images to trick the discriminator, while the discriminator attempts to discern between authentic and fake images. The matched regions created by SURF were used as input to the GAN to determine which region was copied (Real) and which was moved (Fake). The copied regions obtained from the discriminator are considered authentic images, while the forged regions obtained from the generator are considered forged. The generator can learn the pattern distribution of the training images, and the discriminator can extract the feature to characterize the image as real or fake. The training process of a GAN can be described as a two-player min-max game, where the generator tries to maximize the probability that the discriminator makes a mistake, while the discriminator tries to minimize its error rate. This adversarial relationship between the generator and the discriminator is what gives GAN its name. During training, the generator and discriminator are updated iteratively using back propagation. The generator's weights are updated based on the feedback from the discriminator, while the discriminator's weights are updated based on its performance in classifying real and fake images.

Fig. 8. Steps of GAN to classify real or fake images.

GAN is a learning method that maps an image with a random noise denoted z to an authentic image denoted y by $G: \{x, z\} \rightarrow y$. It trains the generator to produce outputs that cannot be distinguished from "real" images by an adversarial discriminator D which is trained to recognize fakes as well as possible. GAN can be expressed by:

$$L_{GAN}(G, D) = E_{x,y} [\log D(x, y)] + E_{x,z} [\log(1 - D(x, G(x, z)))] \quad (7)$$

where G attempts to reduce the expectation value and D attempts to achieve it as follows:

$$G^* = \text{Arg}_{\min_G} \max_D (L_{GAN}(G, D)) \quad (8)$$

Combining the GAN expectation value with a more typical loss, such as the L_2 distance, the discriminator's function persists, but the generator has been assigned to be close to the real output in an L_2 manner. In addition, the possibility of using the L_1 distance denoted by $\|y - G(x, z)\|_1$ rather than the L_2 was investigated, because L_1 encourages less distortion.

$$L_{L1}(G) = E_{x,y,z} [\|y - G(x, z)\|_1] \quad (9)$$

The final G was formulated as:

$$G^* = \text{Arg}_{\min_G} \max_D (L_{GAN}(G, D) + \lambda L_{L1}(G)) \quad (10)$$

The network may still learn how to map from x to y without z , but it would give predictable outputs and consequently refuse to identify any pattern other than a λ value.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The functionality of the proposed method was investigated using two benchmarking databases: CoMoFoD [28] and MICC F220 [29]. The CoMoFoD database was used to detect copy-move forgery by analyzing 260 forged JPG or PNG image sets categorized by manipulation and postprocessing methods, including rotation, scaling, JPEG compression, and blurring. Furthermore, the MICC F220 dataset consists of 220 images, 110 of which are forged and 110 are originals.

A. SLIC Segmentation with SURF Keypoints

Superpixels in an image have perceptual meaning when pixels in the same region share similar visual features. These are joined together to provide a compacted depiction of the objects, which is highly beneficial for detecting copy-move forgeries. This SLIC segmentation technique generates superpixels by grouping pixels based on color and spatial closeness at the image level. It was assumed that the copied and moved regions in the forged image share the same color properties, texture attributes, and shape primitives. To address this issue, SLIC was used to address the color and texture aspects of the suspected regions. The SURF method was used to locate primitive features. Figure 9 shows the extracted SLIC

with SURF features to observe a copy-move forgery. Figure 9(d) shows how duplicated portions with the same keypoints could be helpful in the detection of copy-move forgeries.

Fig. 9. Detection results of CMF using SLIC+SURF: (a) Original image, (b) forged image, and (c), (d) SLIC+SURF.

B. Matching Keypoints Between Copy-Move Regions using SURF

The green rectangle in Figure 10(a) depicts the object in the original image, whereas the red rectangles in Figure 10(b) represent the copy-move forgeries. SURF features in yellow are appropriately connected between duplicated regions.

Fig. 10. SURF features from image: (a) Original image, (b) forged image, and (c) SURF keypoints.

C. Detection of CMF under JPEG Compression

JPEG compression with a Quality Factor (QF) of 20 and 80 for a copy-move region deforms the forged image. A region was copied and pasted into a non-overlapping region at random spatial locations. Figure 11 shows how the proposed method can detect duplicated regions with the maximum True Positive Rate (TPR) and the lowest False Negative Rate (FNR) for all QF s. For a JPEG QF of 20, TPR was 96% and FNR was 3% for the worst case. For a JPEG QF of 80, TPR was 98% and FNR was 2%.

D. Detection of Multiple CMF under Scaling, Blurring, and Rotation

The proposed method was evaluated in terms of postprocessing attacks such as scaling, blur, and rotation. As shown in Figure 12, GAN reduces false matches and significantly improves the visual detection result in both types of postprocessing-based attacks.

Fig. 11. CMFD results based on high and low QF in JPEG compression: (a) Original image, (b) forged image ($QF = 80$), (c) detection results with $QF = 80$, and (d) detection results with $QF = 30$.

E. Performance Evaluation and Discussion

Table I shows the evaluation results of the proposed method and Table II shows a comparison with three recent state-of-the-art methods: (1) segmentation-based [30-31], (2) deep learning-based [32], and (3) keypoint-based [16]. All implementations were carried out in MATLAB using the image processing toolbox. Its performance was measured in terms of Precision (P), Recall (R), and F1-score (F1), as specified below:

$$P = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_p} \times 100\% \tag{11}$$

$$R = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_n} \times 100\% \tag{12}$$

$$F_1\text{-score} = 2 \times \frac{P \times R}{P + R} \times 100\% \tag{13}$$

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented a segmentation concept that exhibits higher discriminative powers compared to a single key point, using SLIC segmentation as a preprocessing technique in

image analysis. Additionally, a SURF key point-based method was implemented for each segmented region in the image. This approach is known for its resilience to translation and post-processing attacks. In addition, a GAN framework was used to reduce the number of false positives. The experimental results confirmed that the proposed method exhibited resilience to rotation, blurring, scaling, and jpg compression, and demonstrated its effectiveness compared to current state-of-the-art approaches.

Fig. 12. Visual detection of multiple CMF under scaling, blurring, and rotation attacks: (a) multiple CMF and 0.6 scaling up factor, (b) multiple CMF and 0.3 scaling down factor, (c) multiple CMF and blurring $\sigma = 0.2$, and (d) multiple CMF and rotation $\theta = 45^\circ$.

TABLE I. THE PROPOSED METHOD'S PERFORMANCE IN DETECTING CMF IN FORGED IMAGES.

Database	SLIC and SURF without GAN			SLIC+SURF with GAN		
	P (%)	R (%)	F1 (%)	P (%)	R (%)	F1 (%)
CoMoFoD [28]	91.41	92.88	91.52	95.51	93.21	94.34
MICC F220 [29]	90.21	90.11	90.42	94.12	93.12	93.62

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON WITH OTHER METHODS

Method	Database	Preprocessing step	Descriptor model	Accuracy	Time (sec)
[30]	CoMoFoD	SLIC segmentation	GLCM	TPR= 93.75 FPR= 7.25 F1=93.75	32.76
[31]	CoMoFoD	DenseNet-41 Segmentation	Mask-RCNN	P=98.12 R= 95.85 F1=96.97	45
[16]	CoMoFoD	SIFT keypoints	Agglomerative Hierarchical Clustering	TPR= 97.65 FPR = 9.02	6120
[32]	CoMoFoD	CNN features	VGG16 & Buster Net DNN	P= 78.22 R= 73.89 F1=75.98	NA
Proposed Method	CoMoFoD	SLIC +SURF	GAN	P=95.51 R=93.21 F1=94.34	40

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Making Different Topographic Maps with the Surfer Package

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to describe the preparation of topographic maps using the Surfer software. A total of 159 regularly distributed Ground Control Points (GCPs) were collected with the use of the Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS). Seven methods (Contour Map, Post Map, 3D Surface Map, 3D Wireframe Maps, Grid Vector-1 Map, Color Relief Map, and Shaded Relief Maps) at the Surfer environment were used to prepare the topographic maps at the Mukhtar Village near the Al-Fallujah City. Contour lines with other features were superimposed on the DEM layer, which refers to the topography of the terrain inside this study area. The accuracy of the database's results was estimated, essential maps were given, and the results were efficient and effective. The most appropriate method to represent topographic maps was proposed, each of these techniques has been enough to provide us with a general understanding of the subject area.

Keywords-topographic map; GCPs; contour map; 3D surface map; Surfer software

I. INTRODUCTION

The topographic map is one of the most often utilized maps. Contours are employed to depict the form and height of the land, including both natural and manufactured features such as valleys, hills, plains, streams, boundaries, and significant buildings [1]. A topographic map accurately depicts the geographical characteristics of an area, such as rivers, lakes, paths, railways, power lines, elevations, and contours. Topographical maps are a useful planning aid and information source [2, 3]. Authors in [4] located the research region using Google Earth, DEM, and satellite pictures together with geological and topographical maps. Techniques of geographic information systems were utilized to compute the major large study's area of coverage and geometrical factors [4].

Digital mapping is a way of compiling and formatting a collection of geographical data from an actual location into a virtual representation. The main purpose of this technology is to create maps that accurately depict a given location while also highlighting all the interesting elements that would be useful to a user. The surfer program supports map projections and selects a map to display from an endless list of projections [5]. The term Digital Elevation Model (DEM) refers to raster files that contain elevation information for each raster cell. DEMs are employed in a variety of applications because knowledge of the slope of the ground is useful for explaining phenomena on the surface and in general understanding the way the terrain works [6]. A DEM is a three-dimensional representation of the earth's surface devoid of any plants and structures. The Digital Surface Model (DSM) is a representation of the entire earth's surface, including all its components. Briefly, all the collected satellite data form first a DSM [7, 8].

Geographic Information Systems (GISs) frequently make use of DEMs, which are also the most frequently utilized foundation for digitally created relief maps. DSM may be helpful for 3D digital city deployments, visualization applications, and landscape modeling [9, 10]. DTM is frequently necessary for geological applications, land-use studies, flood or drainage models, and other uses [11-13]. Traditional survey methods, like leveling as well as total stations, are used to generate DEMs with high accuracy for civil engineering projects, although they are more expensive than other methods. Depending on the length of baselines, geodetic GPS receivers are known to be utilized for locating with centimeter- or millimeter-level accuracy [14, 15]. Land-based GPS is intended to give 3-D location, navigation, and velocity data. Satellites make up the space segment of GPS, while ground-based tracking and monitoring spots and user-based receivers make up the control and user portions. The distances between the reception antenna and the satellites in view are measured by a ground-based static or roaming GPS receiver, which is merely a range measurement device. The location is then calculated from the range vectors' adjusted intersections [16]. In the field of geodetic surveying, the GPS is a highly developed technique. The GPS method is significantly more effective than more similar methods, including total station, level, and theodolite, in terms of the number of users, effective cost, inter-visibility, and accuracy [17-20]. Authors in [21] proved that produced DEM using DGPS data are more effective than DEM produced using contour separation or SRTM data. Authors in [22] utilized RTK-DGPS data gathering for leveling, local study, and the application of 2D polynomial models and Earth Gravitational Models (EGM2008, EGM96), dictated by geoid undulation. When the

data do not entirely cover the study domain, interpolation may be utilized. This situation might occur to illustrate changes in the height of the land surface (DEMs) [23]. There are different interpolation principles for the interpolation methods, and each of them may produce different results. Some of these methods include linear interpolation, kriging, triangulation, natural neighbor, Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), and polynomial regression [24, 25]. In [17], various surface modeling techniques were employed, including nearest neighbor, natural neighbor, and IDW.

Golden Software provides two products: Grapher TM for 2D and 3D graphing and Surfer for gridding, contouring, and 3D surface mapping. Surfer is strong contouring, gridding, and surface mapping software for scientists, engineers, teachers, and anybody else who wants to create maps quickly and efficiently. The grid-based mapping tool Surfer interpolates randomly spaced Cartesian data into a grid with uniform spacing. The grid is used to create a variety of maps, like contour, color relief, and 3D surface maps [26]. With Surfer, numerous map kinds can be produced, altered, and presented. These maps come in a variety of formats, including base, contour, post, classified post, 3D surface, 3-D wireframe, color relief, grids values, peak and depressions, pointed cloud, watershed, and view shed maps [27-29].

II. STUDY AREA

Information was gathered using a Differential GPS (DGPS) survey carried out in Mukhtar Village near Al-Fallujah City as illustrated in Figure. A total of 159 Ground Control's Points were observed using DGPS technology (Topcon GR3/Hipper II). These observed points are included in Appendix A and can be seen in Figure 1 as contour lines. The purpose of the study is to create a topographical map by using the Surfer package in order to know the terrain and the areas of elevation.

Fig. 1. Study area.

III. RESULT: MAP TYPES

Different topographic maps can be created, modified, and displayed with Surfer software for comparative analysis. After the topographic map representation was done, the Contour Map was found as more suitable, as shown in Figures 2-8.

Fig. 2. Contour Map.

Fig. 3. Post Map.

Fig. 4. 3D Surface Map.

Fig. 5. 3D Wireframe Map.

Fig. 6. Grid Vector Map.

Fig. 7. Color Relief Map.

Fig. 8. Shaded Relief Map.

The surfer can conduct volumetric calculations quickly. Cross-sectional profiles can be computed and exported as well. Figure 9 shows the mass haul diagram for the road that passes throughout at a minimum elevation of 48.3 m and a maximum elevation of 50.7 m. The report for the Grid Volumetric Computations results that Volume [Cut] $\approx 666.962 \text{ m}^3$, and Volume [fill] $\approx 5026.602 \text{ m}^3$. According to the Grid Data Report, the contour map had the lowest possible error value whereas the Grid Vectors Map had the highest, as shown in Table I. The error values for each type of map are not considered a criterion for choosing the type of map representation due to the existence of limitations, such as the purpose of the map and the number of points. Authors in [23, 30] mentioned that the topographic maps and their calculation can be performed quickly in Surfer. The gridding files for each map can be edited, combined, filtered, sliced, queried, and mathematically transformed. There is no difference in opinion with previous works. The results of this study encourage the expansion of applied ideas in the future by integrating with other programs and result comparison.

Fig. 9. The surfer volumetric calculations the mass haul diagram.

TABLE I. ERROR VALUE FOR EACH MAP TYPE

Type	No. of points	RMSE
Contour Map	159	0.016~0.025
Post Map	159	0.290~0.297
3D Surface Map	159	0.206~0.213
3D wireframe Map	159	0.283~0.296
Grid vector Map	159	0.355-0.367
Color Relief Map	159	0.295-0.301
Shaded Relief Map	159	0.310-0.322

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, topographic maps of the Mukhtar Village near Al-Fallujah City were drawn. Most of the study area is characterized by roughly equal levels on the right side of the map with a gentle slope on the most part, as the elevations appeared to increase as we go to the left of the map. The produced maps exhibit the accuracy and ease of the Surfer package and its ability to draw many types of topographic maps.

The main contributions of this study is the possibility of using its results in many areas, e.g. the street construction, laying water pipes or sanitary sewers, or being used as a preliminary study of a site when adding or creating a building. The Contour Map is the optimum for usage with the given features on the mapped area.

APPENDIX

Some of the data taken from the study site using the DGPS are shown in the following table:

Point	Coordinates		
	East-m	North-m	Elevation-m
1	385972.7	3693026	50.673
2	385972.8	3693026	50.663
3	385972.8	3693026	50.659
4	385972.8	3693026	50.671
5	385972.4	3693027	50.646
6	385971.8	3693027	50.579
7	385971.4	3693029	50.625
8	385971.1	3693030	50.431
9	385970.7	3693032	50.51
10	385970.4	3693033	50.403
11	385970	3693034	50.259
12	385969.7	3693036	50.086
13	385969.3	3693037	49.885
14	385969	3693038	49.616
15	385968.6	3693039	49.363
16	385968.5	3693040	49.238
17	385968.2	3693042	48.9
18	385968	3693044	48.853
19	385967.7	3693045	48.802
20	385967.3	3693047	48.683
21	385967	3693048	48.681
22	385966.7	3693049	48.653
23	385966.5	3693051	48.729
24	385966.2	3693053	48.644
25	385965.8	3693054	48.589
26	385965.4	3693055	48.625
27	385965	3693059	48.551
28	385964.3	3693061	48.49
29	385963.4	3693064	48.499
30	385963.2	3693065	48.482
31	385962.4	3693071	48.423
32	385962	3693074	48.509
33	385961.2	3693079	48.621
34	385960.5	3693084	48.711
35	385959.9	3693086	48.785
36	385958.6	3693093	48.873
37	385958.4	3693094	48.887
38	385957.4	3693101	48.934
39	385956.5	3693105	49.025
40	385955.3	3693110	48.917
41	385954.2	3693114	48.9
42	385953.3	3693117	48.768
43	385952.5	3693121	48.775
44	385951.8	3693122	48.794
45	385949.9	3693122	48.72
46	385945.8	3693122	48.738
47	385942.9	3693122	48.655
48	385937.4	3693121	48.74
49	385933.5	3693121	48.733
50	385929.7	3693120	48.761

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A Resonator Noise Reduction Solution for a Centrifugal Gas Compressor

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this work is to reduce the noise generated by a compressor that conveys methane gas. After certain measurements were conducted a high level of noise was observed in the 2000-3000 Hz range, therefore a solution for noise reduction at the source is addressed and presented in this paper. The research method is based on designing resonators to be applied on the stator of a centrifugal compressor used in a natural gas distribution station. First, the calculations are made on resonators with air as the working fluid and then are validated through real measurements in a Kundt tube. After validation, the working fluid is changed with gas, calculations are made once again, and acoustic simulations are performed. To facilitate acoustic simulations and reduce computational time, a simplified stator geometry was employed. This simplified model encompassed the region starting from the rotor's gas exit, where the resonators were deployed. The purpose of the acoustic simulation was to validate the frequency range influenced by the resonators and to estimate the overall noise reduction. Depending on the operating regime of the compressor, the rotor fundamental can vary within the frequency domain of 2000 – 3000 Hz. This broadband domain requires the usage of several resonators with different resonant frequencies. The proposed solution obtained an average value of attenuation, excluding the peaks of the attenuation, in the frequency domain of 2000 - 3000 Hz, of 9 dBA. If the fundamental frequency coincides with a resonance of the resonator, higher attenuation can occur. Also, fundamental attenuation can lead to attenuation of the harmonics.

Keywords-centrifugal gas compressor; noise; acoustic; reduction; resonator keyword

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural gas will become the second major energy source by 2030, its consumption rate will be the same as that of oil by 2040 while it will surpass oil and become the largest energy consumer by 2050 [1, 2]. Methane gas is a raw material for the production of other environmentally friendly fuels such as hydrogen that will constitute the fuels of the future. Therefore in [3] a methodical optimization process was devised,

employing multivariate regression models created by combining input parameters within an idealized reactor.

Natural gas compressor, as a piece of important pressurizing equipment, usually has a high rotation speed, generally between 3000 and 6000 rpm, and is an important branch of rotating machinery. In [4], high-frequency measurements were utilized to investigate the occurrence of rotating instability and the onset of spike-type stall in a high-speed compressor. Depending on the compressor speed and the

impellers blade number, the Blade Pass Frequency (BPF) usually falls in the 1000 - 4500 Hz frequency domain. Such reduction can be observed in [5] where the aim was to enhance the eco-friendliness of compressors and thus duct resonator acoustic arrays were designed to reduce the acoustic energy released into the environment. The human ear is most sensitive to frequencies between 2,000 and 5,000 Hz, so with the BPF falling in this domain it is easy to understand why it is considered annoying. BPF is thought to be the most critical contributor at the general noise level recorded at centrifugal compressors and its noise components originate from the upstream and downstream of the impeller circumferential flow distortions [6]. Compressor BPF for marine diesel engine turbochargers is numerically studied and experimentally investigated in [7].

Centrifugal compressors use the mechanical energy to compress the working fluid and a small fraction of it is converted into acoustic energy, which consequently propagates in the whole system as noise [8]. The excessive noise of the industrial compressors used in the gas transport systems is one of the problems that both industrial areas and its populated neighborhoods are confronted with. Equipment noise reduction represents a challenge because that noise has a big impact on the staff serving these turbo-machineries and the nearby urban areas, as well. Different solutions have been proposed to eliminate centrifugal compressors noise among which one can mention the use of passive techniques (porous absorbing panels, resonators cavities) or active techniques (active noise cancelation). In [9], a methodology for experimental validation of a CFD model for predicting noise generation in centrifugal compressors is presented. In [10], a 3-dimensional CFD model of a centrifugal compressor is analyzed and in [11] fluid phenomena related to whoosh noise are studied. In [12], an experimental investigation on the metal foam for controlling centrifugal fan noise is presented. In [13], the aerodynamic noise of a turbocharger compressor mounted on a passenger car engine is examined by using turbulence numerical simulation, aero-acoustic simulation, and acoustic Boundary Element Method (BEM).

Vibration and noise characteristic of two-stage centrifugal compressors used in a refrigeration system are experimentally studied in [14] where a multi-layer micro-perforated panel absorber fixed at the outlet pipe is employed to attenuate the compressor noise. The experimental results confirm that the designed absorber can effectively reduce the noise of the centrifugal refrigeration compressor.

Most of the published studies on noise reduction of centrifugal compressors using resonator arrays were found with resonators applied at silencers, as in [15]. There testing confirmed that the duct resonator array reduces narrowband noise by at least 14 dB within the specified bandwidth (2-3 kHz) and can lower broadband noise by up to 8 dB (1-2 kHz), at pipe level [16]. A similar observation was made in [17] where the acoustic performance of the Helmholtz array ranged from 9 to 13.2 dB for the vaned diffuser.

Regarding noise reduction at centrifugal compressors, authors in [18] proposed that the resonators should be applied on the compressor stator, in the region where the air comes out

from the rotor. In this respect, a series of resonators were applied on the stator and therefore an array of acoustic resonators that attenuate the acoustic energy generated by the impeller was formed. Starting from the idea of applying resonators on the stator, the present case study is based on their application on the stator of a centrifugal compressor, which is a part of a natural gas distribution station. Given the growth of the urban area that is in the vicinity of the distribution station, the noise levels recorded in the station perimeter often exceed the legislation limits. The solution is based on designing resonators to be applied on the stator of the centrifugal compressor used in a natural gas distribution station.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology applied in this study relies on four well defined steps. In the first step, as a starting point of the entire research, the problem is defined by establishing the frequency of interest. Solution designing as a second step is followed by design validation with air as the working fluid and the final step consists in applying the solution for the gas case. Three measurements were performed at different regimes (chosen based on the recorded statistics), with the compressor having a number of blades $nb = 13$, compressor shaft speed N between 9000 and 14000 rpm (150-233 Hz), obtaining a BPF between 2000 and 3000 Hz (N^*), which is henceforth considered the frequency domain of interest, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. BPF variation at different regimes.

Step two consists in defining the analytic model for calculating the resonators. It is generally known that the resonator is an acoustic system encompassing a rigid-walled cavity filled with air and a neck through which the cavity communicates. When pressure is applied, the air filling at the neck starts to move back and forth, damping out in time. There are many studies where Helmholtz resonators are analyzed. In [19], a promising design of sound absorption panels containing acoustic resonators is proposed. In [20], focus is given on an optimized method for Helmholtz Resonators (HRs) designed to be used in room acoustics. This method utilizes a transfer matrix and the electro-acoustic analogy whereas the calculations optimization was conducted by integrating the measured data to enhance the consistency between the calculated sound absorption coefficient and the measurements taken in the reverberation room. In [21], an HR with a spiral neck is studied theoretically and numerically. Also, ways to achieve significant sound reduction in a compact solution at

lower frequencies while exhibiting multiple resonance at higher frequencies are studied. For an individual resonator, it is known that the acoustic absorption is selective, meaning that it works only in a specific frequency. It can be calculated by:

$$f_0 = \frac{c}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{A}{V \cdot (+0.8d)}} \quad (1)$$

where c represents the sound speed, d is the resonator's neck diameter, while V is the resonator's volume.

On the other hand, to obtain a better performance in terms of larger frequency coverage, resonators with perforated plate can be used. These types of resonant structures are made of coupled resonators acquired by placing a perforated plate at a certain distance from a rigid wall. The impedance of the perforated panel Z_{pp} is computed using the Maa model [22]:

$$Z_{pp} = \frac{32 \mu t}{\sigma d^2} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{s^2}{32}} + \frac{\sqrt{2}sd}{32t} \right) + \frac{j\omega t \rho_0}{\sigma} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3^2 + \frac{s}{2}}} + 0.85 \frac{d}{t} \right) \quad (2)$$

where μ is air viscosity [Pa/s], σ represents the porosity of the perforated panel, s is the perforation constant, equal to $10d\sqrt{f}$, ω is the angular frequency [rad/s], ρ_0 is the air density inside the perforations [kg/m^3], d is the diameter of the perforations [m], t is the distance between the centers of two perforations [m], and j represents the imaginary part of the impedance.

The total impedance of the resonator is the sum of the perforated panel and the back cavity impedances:

$$Z_{\text{back_air}} = -i \rho_0 c_0 \cot(kD) s \quad (3)$$

$$Z_{\text{total}} = Z_{M(MPP)} + Z_{\text{back_air}} \quad (4)$$

where k is the wave number and D is the cavity depth. From the total system impedance, the acoustic reflection coefficient at normal incidence is determined, from which the acoustic absorption coefficient is:

$$R = \frac{(Z_{\text{total}} - \rho_0 c_0)}{(Z_{\text{total}} + \rho_0 c_0)} \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha = 1 - |R|^2 \quad (6)$$

Figure 2 presents a comparison in frequency-amplitude response between an individual resonator and the perforated plate. There the main difference consists in a broadband response of the perforated plate but with smaller absorption capacity due to the perforations interaction. One of the problems when designing a resonator is given by the impurities and dirt which can be found in our specific case in gas. Designing a resonator with small neck diameter could lead to clogging of the perforation reducing the acoustic treatment effectiveness. So, a compromise between the available space and the above resonator design solutions had to be made.

In order to cover the entire domain, four frequencies were selected as references at the resonators design. These

resonators were applied on the stator of the compressor, as presented in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Working frequency domain for the two types of resonators.

Fig. 3. Stator segment (top – no resonator applied, bottom – highlighted resonators on the stator).

Step three consisted in validating the selected solutions by means of measurements. For this step, the resonators frequencies were modeled for air ($c = 340$ m/s) and were manufactured from a thermoplastic aliphatic polyester (PLA, Poly) at the 3D printer, as in Figure 4. The resonators were measured in impedance tube, Figure 5, using ISO 10534-2 method that is based on transfer function between the two microphones. Moreover, the reflection coefficient, from which the acoustic absorption coefficient is resulted, is calculated [22].

Fig. 4. Resonators designed for 2000 Hz – 2600 Hz.

Fig. 5. Resonator tests in impedance tube.

In Figure 6, one can easily see that the designed resonators reduce the noise at the intended frequency, therefore the design principles were appropriately chosen, even though small deviations (max. deviation obtained: 18Hz) due to the manufacturing process were spotted.

Fig. 6. Acoustic absorption coefficient for the four resonators (case: air).

Step four was to model and optimize a series of resonators for gas compressor for a speed of sound in methane of $c = 462$ m/s ($\lambda_{\text{methane}} > \lambda_{\text{air}}$). In order to evaluate the noise reduction of resonators for gas compressor, a finite element method was used. For acoustic simulations, a simplified geometry of the stator was utilized so as to reduce the time calculation. A simplified model was made for a region chosen from the exit of the gas from the rotor (see Figure 3), where the resonators were applied. The objective of the acoustic simulation was to verify the frequency domain on which the resonators act and to estimate an overall noise reduction.

It is known that similar resonators must not be placed very close to each other because they interfere, and their efficiency is lowered. When having two similar resonators close to one another the frequency for which they were designed is shifted and as consequence the system does not work on the intended frequency domain. Even a relation between resonators holes and high TL (Transmission Loss) for a given frequency domain was defined in [23]. In this case, it cannot be applied due to the small distances available in the stator region. Given the specific geometry of the compressor stator, three solutions were proposed for resonator placing (in line of slightly shifted between them), see Figure 7. The mesh of the selected domains is presented in Figure 8.

Fig. 7. CAD simplified model (top: front view, bottom: side view).

Fig. 8. Mesh of the simplified stator CAD model.

Numerical simulations were performed by ACTRAN software, which uses the Finite Element Method. For this problem the acoustic module was used and the wave propagation was employed. The mesh was modeled by a rule of 8 tetrahedral elements per the wavelength of the highest studied frequency. Considering a speed of sound of 462 m/s and a

maximum frequency of 2800 Hz, the wavelength is 0.165 m, which leads to a maximum element dimension of 0.02 m. Special attention was given to the calculation grid in the area of the resonator perforations (the neck of the resonator), in order to be able to capture the visco-thermal phenomena that occur when the resonance is reached. Thus, elements with dimensions up to 0.3 mm were utilized in the resonators neck.

The applied boundary conditions in FEM software were: the bottom surface of the mesh was considered as the plane wave acoustic excitation, the properties of methane were applied to the fluid, and the surface above was considered a free field surface with no reflection back into the computational grid. Therefore, the acoustic TL was computed knowing the acoustic power generated and the acoustic power transmitted out of the model. All the other surfaces were considered as hard walls with perfect reflection.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The acoustic simulations results highlighted once more that the position of the resonators influences both the acting frequency of the resonators and their effectiveness (Figure 9). The objective of this work was to achieve the highest attenuation in the frequency domain of 2000-3000Hz. Consequently the first version (V1) with the resonators in straight line, obtained the highest attenuation in this domain.

Fig. 9. Transmission loss obtained for the simplified model.

For a better understanding of the shift in the resonant frequencies of the resonators and the difference of attenuation level for each resonator, an acoustic pressure plot inside the fluid domain of the V1 is presented in Figure 10.

At the frequency of 2000 Hz, the acoustic pressure inside the first resonator is in the opposite phase with the generated wave and the resonator competence is high. Also, in the resonators' neck, the acoustic velocity of the air is high and this can lead to interferences between the resonators. Only the second resonator is situated in pre-resonance domain leading to a small influence on the effectiveness of the first resonator. At the other frequencies, the resonators with lower frequency produce a phase modification that influences both attenuation and resonant frequency.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Depending on the operating regime of the compressor, the rotor fundamental frequency can vary within the frequency domain of 2000 – 3000 Hz. This broad band domain requires

the usage of several resonators with different resonant frequencies. The proposed solution obtained an average value of attenuation of 9 dB, excluding the peaks of the attenuation, in the frequency domain of 2000 - 3000 Hz. If the fundamental coincides with a resonance frequency of a resonator, higher attenuation can occur, but also fundamental attenuation can lead to attenuation of the harmonics. Different geometrical arrangements of resonators were performed, and the results obtained by numerical simulation and experimental evaluation provide a way for topological optimization.

Fig. 10. Sound pressure field inside the V1 model.

The acquired results are encouraging for the continuation of the research, even if from a technological point of view, the proposed solution is not so easy to be applied at the moment.

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Effects of Geometry Design Parameters on the Fatigue Failure of a Drive Axle Housing using Finite Element Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The current paper investigates the effects of geometric design parameters on the fatigue failure of the drive axle housing using the Finite Element Method (FEM). The study examines the effects of various factors on the fatigue life of the drive axle housing, such as axle housing wall thickness, housing cross-sectional rounding radius, and rounding radius of the central part of the housing. Based on the known material properties and dynamic loads, a CAD/FEM model of the drive axle housing was developed, and a structural analysis was carried out. Based on the results of the structural analysis, critical places on the housing were determined, and fatigue analysis and lifetime prediction were performed. Through a series of simulations, the study reveals that increasing housing wall thickness can significantly improve fatigue performance. Similarly, increasing the rounding radius at the housing cross-section, as well as the rounding radius at the central part of the housing can also lead to improved fatigue performance. However, the effect of increasing the value of these two radii is not as significant as the effect of the wall thickness. These findings give useful information regarding the design and manufacture of drive axle housings for vehicles, intending to reduce the likelihood of fatigue failure.

Keywords-drive axle housing; fatigue failure; finite element analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

During the vehicle service life, dynamic forces caused by road roughness create dynamic stresses that lead to fatigue failure of the drive axle housing. Therefore, it is vital that the drive axle housing resists fatigue failure for its intended service life [1]. Also, it is necessary that the strength and stiffness of the drive axle housing meets the specified service requirements [2]. Due to its importance in the vehicle, the drive axle housing is a constant topic of research, especially from the aspect of fatigue failure analysis. It is stated in [3] that the welding procedures affect the occurrence of fatigue cracks in the drive axle housing of heavy trucks. Based on fracture mechanics, authors in [4] analyzed the occurrence of fatigue cracks on the drive axle housing of a crane truck. The four-point bending fatigue test of the drive axle housing assembly using the Finite Element (FE)-integrated fatigue analysis methodology was simulated in [5]. The presented technique is based on the local stress and strain approach in combination with two critical plane damage parameters. Authors in [6] studied the drive axle housing fracture of a mining dump truck based on the load spectrum. In order to determine the causes that affect the drive axle housing dynamic stress, the road slope, any uneven load and eccentricity are analyzed using the finite element method. Authors [7] performed deterministic and probabilistic fatigue life calculations of a damaged welded joint in the construction of the rear axle of a trolleybus. In their study, they state that the main purpose of the calculation was to determine whether in-service failure could be predicted (and prevented) during the design phase and what was their main cause. Authors in [8] studied the dynamic response and fatigue life prediction of a vehicle system under a random road spectrum and analyzed the dynamic stress magnitude and fatigue life in the resonant frequency region. Authors in [9] used ABAQUS software to analyze the dynamic and static characteristics and fatigue analysis of car drive axle housing under sinusoidal load spectrum, obtain plots of the location and life distribution of the fracture zone, and propose improvement plans.

Authors in [10] took the drive axle housing of a light truck as the research object, and chose the design parameters, permitted stress, and displacement with least weight as the optimization goal. Authors in [11] analyzed the dynamic characteristics and fatigue of the drive axle housing and carried out a lightweight optimization design to verify the optimized drive shaft housing. Authors in [12] presented a reliability analysis method based on the Monte Carlo technique by studying the optimization scheme of the drive axle housing of off-road vehicles. Based on this, lightweight design was carried out and the weight of the drive axle housing was reduced by 12.48%. Authors in [13] carried out Six Sigma multi-objective lightweight drive axle housing design, studied the influence of drive axle housing wall thickness on its performance using entropy weight methods and TOPSIS, and combined RBF and NSGA-II algorithms to design a multi-purpose lightweight drive axle housing, which significantly improved performance. To study the vertical fatigue of the drive axle housing, authors in [14] proposed a seven degree of freedom dynamic model to predict fatigue failure under dynamic load and presented an optimization scheme based on this.

Furthermore, numerous studies have examined the effects of geometric design parameters on the structural failure due to fatigue [15-18]. The abovementioned research was mainly aimed at examining the influence of various factors on the service life of the drive axle housing, such as driving conditions, vehicle load, material properties, and axle housing manufacturing technology. The aim of this paper is to investigate the influence of geometric design parameters on the fatigue failure of the drive axle housing using the FEM. The design parameters that were taken into account during the analysis are the thickness of the axle housing wall, the rounding radius at the cross section of the axle housing, and the rounding radius at the central part of the axle housing.

II. DEVELOPMENT OF THE CAD/FEM MODEL

The CATIA V5 software package was used during the development of the CAD/FEM model of the drive axle housing. After the CAD model of the housing was formed (Figure 1), the material of the housing (S460N) with the mechanical properties shown in Table I was defined.

Fig. 1. CAD model of the drive axle housing.

TABLE I. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HOUSING MATERIAL S460N

Young's modulus of elasticity	E	208.5 GPa
Yield strength	S_y	497.5 MPa
Poisson's coefficient	ν	0.3
Brinell Hardness number	HB	190
Shear modulus	G	73 GPa
Tensile strength	S_{ut}	629.9 MPa
Strain at brake point	ϵ_{max}	26.8 %
Shear strength	SS	390 MPa
Density	ρ	7860 kg/m ³

After the CAD model of the housing was formed, FEM modeling was performed in the Generative Structural Analysis module. The first step in the FEM modeling is discretization and selection of finite elements, where FEs of the parabolic type (TE10) tetrahedron were used. The size of the element was 9 mm with an absolute sag value of 1.8 mm.

After discretization, it is necessary to define the load acting on the drive axle housing. The drive axle housing is loaded with bending stress due to the weight of the truck with the trailer. The intensity of the load is defined according to the legal requirements and the axle configuration of the truck

whose drive axle housing is the subject of analysis. According to regulations [19], maximum load of the drive axle, i.e. the drive axle housing in which the drive axle is located, must not exceed 113 kN. Therefore, a load of 56.5 kN was applied in the form of concentrated axial forces at the places where vehicle pneumatic suspension system is attached (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. Defining of boundary and loading conditions.

After defining the load, the boundary conditions are defined (housing supports). The housing is supported on the places where the bearings are located. It was necessary to define the previously created virtual part using the Rigid Virtual Part command. Then, using the Pivot command, boundary conditions were defined in such a way that rotation of the housing around the z axis was allowed. After the FEM modeling of the drive axle housing in the CATIA V5 software package, structural analysis was performed for the given load. During the structural analysis, the von Mises stress values generated on the housing were monitored, along with the displacement values (Figures 3 and 4).

Fig. 3. Von Mises stress distribution.

As can be seen from Figure 3, the von Mises stresses are mainly distributed in the places of the hollow square cross-section, and at the transitions towards the middle part of the drive axle housing where final drive is located. The extreme value of the von Mises stress is 260.19 MPa and is located exactly at the mentioned place of the housing, which is exposed to tension. The stress values that occur at the walls of the hollow square cross-section are in the range of 90 MPa to 155 MPa, depending on the distance from the point of action of the load. The smallest stresses, as expected, occur at the points of support and are negligible. It can be seen from Figure 4 that the largest displacements of 3.12 mm, as expected, occur towards the middle of the drive axle housing. Moving towards the ends of the housing, i.e. towards the support places, the displacements decrease.

Fig. 4. Displacement distribution.

III. FATIGUE LIFETIME PREDICTION

Fatigue analysis and fatigue lifetime prediction of the drive axle housing were performed in the Solidworks software package, based on the previously performed structural analysis. The estimate of the fatigue limit S'_e is given as:

$$S'_e = 0.504 S_{ut} \tag{1}$$

for steels with tensile strength up to 1400 MPa [20]. This represents fatigue strength at 10^6 cycles and above. To predict the axle housing fatigue life in the range of 10^5 - 10^6 cycles, the S-N curve of the housing material was evaluated using a practical method [21] with data obtained from tensile testing. S'_e represents the fatigue limit of ideal laboratory specimens. To predict the fatigue limit S_e of actual mechanical component, S'_e must be multiplied by several correction factors that represent the influences of design, manufacturing, and environment on fatigue strength [22]. S_e is defined as:

$$S_e = k_a k_b k_c k_d k_e S'_e \tag{2}$$

where k_a represents the surface factor depending on the surface treatment. It is defined as:

$$k_a = a S_{ut}^b \tag{3}$$

Since the surface roughness of the shell is similar to hot rolled steel sheet after hot stamping, the recommended values are $a = 57.7$ and $b = -0.718$ [23], so the value of the factor k_a is 0.564 for $S_{ut} = 629.9$ MPa. In addition, the housing surfaces are subjected to steel shot blasting to increase housing lifespan. This process may increase lifespan by 70% [21]. Therefore, in the fatigue analysis, the value for k_a used is 0.959. For non-round cross sections, the size factor k_b can be taken as 0.75 for values of the cross-section depth h greater than 50 mm. The load factor k_c is 1 for the bending load. The temperature factor k_d is 1 for the ambient temperature range of $T = 0-250^\circ\text{C}$ [24]. Static FEM analysis showed that there are areas of stress concentration at certain parts of the housing. Therefore, apart from the aforementioned correction factors, the correction factor for the fatigue strength k_e should be taken into account. This correction factor is taken through the static stress concentration factor K_t , which is related to the fatigue stress concentration factor K_f . Therefore, k_e is calculated as:

$$k_e = \frac{1}{K_f} \tag{4}$$

It can be assumed that K_f is equal to K_t [23]. Due to the dimensions and complexity of the housing shape, K_t cannot be derived from the data in the literature but is defined as:

$$K_t = \frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_n} \tag{5}$$

where σ_p is the maximum stress at the stress concentration point, and σ_n is the nominal stress that would have been present if stress concentration had not occurred [21, 25]. The stress σ_p was determined by the previous FEM analysis and is calculated as 260.19 MPa, while the stress σ_n is calculated by considering the drive axle housing as a simple beam with a uniform cross-section box profile loaded by pure bending. So, it is defined as:

$$\sigma_n = \frac{M}{W_x} \tag{6}$$

where M is the bending moment, and W_x is the section modulus of housing cross-section. Therefore, based on the nominal stress value of $\sigma_n = 305$ MPa, we get $K_t \approx K_f = 1.181$ and $k_e = 0.846$. With regard to the correction factors, the $S-N$ curve is defined in Solidworks (Figure 5).

Fig. 5. S-N curve of S460N.

The S-N curve shows that the stress amplitude of the element depends on the number of cycles during its lifespan. The number of cycles is required as input data so that the fatigue analysis of the drive axle housing can be performed. In addition to the S-N curve, it is necessary to define the number of cycles to which the housing is exposed, as well as the loading pattern. The drive axle housing bore load history is a non-zero mean random load. The Goodman mean stress theory is used to correct the non-equal amplitude stress and set the type of analysis to stress life [26]. The number of cycles is set to 109 in the safety factor analysis module [2].

IV. RESULTS

The results of the carried out fatigue analysis of the initial design of the drive axle housing are presented in Figure 6. The probability of the initial crack occurring at the highest stress point is shown in Figure 6(a). The number of cycles at which the crack appears is shown in Figure 6(b) (61936 cycles). Based on the results of the fatigue analysis of the initial design of the drive axle housing and the observed fact that the hollow square cross-section is the critical point of construction, measures were taken to extend the lifespan of the drive axle housing.

Fig. 6. Initial design of drive axle housing: (a) probability of initial crack occurrence, (b) number of cycles until fatigue failure occurs.

Fig. 7. Design of drive axle housing with increased wall thickness: (a) probability of initial crack occurrence, (b) number of cycles until fatigue failure occurs.

The first modification of the existing structure, in order to extend the lifespan of the drive axle housing, is to increase the thickness of the wall of the hollow square cross-section, which represents a critical place on the structure in terms of lifespan. The wall thickness was increased from 8 mm to 9 mm, and the results are presented in Figure 7. The second modification of the existing structure is to increase the rounding radius of the hollow square cross-section of the housing. The inner and outer

rounding radii are increased by the same value, in order to maintain the same cross-sectional wall thickness. The inner rounding radius was increased from 10 mm to 13 mm, while the outer radius increased from 18 mm to 21 mm. The results are presented in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Design of drive axle housing with increased rounding radius of the housing cross-section: (a) probability of initial crack occurrence, (b) number of cycles until fatigue failure occurs.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF STRUCTURAL AND FATIGUE ANALYSIS

Design	Von Mises stress (MPa)	Percentage change (%)	Displacement (mm)	Percentage change (%)	Number of cycles (-)	Percentage change (%)
Initial	260.19	-	3.12	-	61936	-
With increased wall thickness	231.17	-11.2	2.91	-6.7	159175	157
With increased rounding radius of the axle housing cross-section	254.43	-2.2	3.14	0.6	82365	33
With increased rounding radius of the central part of the axle housing	254.04	-2.4	2.99	-4.2	81807	32

The third modification of the existing structure, in order to extend the lifespan of the drive axle housing, is to increase the rounding radius of the central part of the housing. The inner and outer radii are increased by the same value, in order to maintain the same cross-sectional wall thickness. The inner radius was increased from 222 mm to 252 mm, while the outer radius was increased from 230 mm to 260 mm. The results are presented in Figure 9. The results of the structural and fatigue analysis of the initial design of the drive axle housing, along with the modified designs of axle housing, are shown in Table II.

Fig. 9. Design of drive axle housing with increased rounding radius of the central part of the housing: (a) probability of initial crack occurrence, (b) number of cycles until fatigue failure occurs.

V. DISCUSSION

The structural analysis of the initial design of the drive axle housing showed critical locations where fatigue failure occurs. That critical place is at the transition from the hollow square cross-section to the central part of the axle housing where the final drive is located, on the side of housing that is exposed to tension. The number of cycles that the specified location can withstand before the first crack appears is 61936. In order to extend the lifespan of the axle housing, certain geometric changes were made.

The simplest way to increase fatigue strength is to increase the wall thickness of the axle housing. When increasing wall thickness by 1 mm, the value of the maximum stress decreased from 260.19 MPa to 231.17 MPa, representing a decrease of 11.2%. There was also a reduction in displacement from 3.12 mm to 2.91 mm, which represents a reduction of 6.7%. This greatly contributed to the increased lifespan of the structure from the initial 61936 to 159175 cycles, which represents an increase of 157%. On the other hand, the increase in the axle housing wall thickness causes an unnecessary increase in the weight of the housing, from 166.58 kg to 169.07 kg, which represents an increase of 1.5%. An alternative to this is to reduce the stress concentration through geometric redesign. Smoother transition geometry can offer increased lifespan without additional weight.

Looking at the results of the structural and fatigue analysis of the design with an increased rounding radius of the axle housing cross-section, a change of maximum stress from 260.19 MPa to 254.43 MPa, which represents a decrease of 2.2%, can be noticed. On the other hand, there was a slight increase in displacement from 3.12 mm to 3.14 mm (0.6%). By increasing the rounding radius of the cross-section, the lifespan

of the structure is increased from the initial 61936 to 82365 cycles (33% increase), while the weight of the axle housing remains unchanged.

Looking at the results of the structural and fatigue analysis of the design with an increased rounding radius of the central part of axle housing, similar trends as in the previous case can be noticed. There is a 2.4% decrease of maximum stress from 260.19 MPa to 254.04 MPa. On the other hand, unlike the previous case, there is a reduction in displacement from 3.12 mm to 2.99 mm (4.2%). Similar to the previous case, by increasing the rounding radius of the central part of the axle housing, the lifespan of the structure is increased from the initial 61936 to 81807 cycles, representing an increase of 32%, while the weight of the axle housing remains unchanged.

VI. CONCLUSION

Analysis of the geometric design parameters for the fatigue failure of the drive axle housing led to the following conclusions:

- Increasing the wall thickness significantly reduces the stress level that occurs at the axle housing, especially in critical areas with maximal loads. This contributes to increased lifespan of the housing and improves fatigue strength, but also increases the weight of the housing.
- Increasing the rounding radius of the cross-section of the axle housing, the stress concentration is reduced. This results in an increased lifespan of the axle housing without increasing its weight.
- Increasing the rounding radius of the central part of the axle housing positively affects the reduction of stress concentration, which achieves a better distribution of stress through the structure. This ultimately results in an increased service life of the housing without increasing its weight.

As a result of this research, designers and engineers in the automotive industry are equipped with evidence-based guidelines for optimizing driveshaft housing design. By applying the knowledge gained from this study, manufacturers can extend the lifespan and the reliability of the axle housing, consequently improving the overall performance, safety and longevity of the vehicle.

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Friction Behavior of Anodic Oxide Layer Coating on 2017A T4 Aluminum Alloy under Severe Friction Solicitation: The Effect of Anodizing Parameters

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to highlight the wear mechanisms and friction behavior of the 2017A T4 anodized aluminum alloy used for automotive and aerospace applications. The effect of the processing parameters on the durability of the anodized layer under high friction is studied. Scratch tests were carried out to study the level of the friction coefficient with the increase in the thickness of the oxide layer formed on the Al 2017 A (AU4G) substrate. The results of the scratch tests show that the variation in the anodization duration, which influences the thickness of the oxide layer, induces an increase in the coefficient of friction. Besides, the variations in friction coefficient with sliding distance are influenced by the changes in wear morphology and degree of oxidation. Treated surfaces with a thickness of 50 μm have the lowest friction coefficients and wear rates. Their improved wear resistance may be related to the increased bond strength compared to other anodized surfaces. The tribological damage was characterized by the detachment of debris, which increases with the increase of the duration of anodization. Upon sliding, its detachment leads to delamination of the underlying anodic aluminum oxides and subsequent abrasion of the aluminum substrate.

Keywords-aluminum alloy; anodizing parameters; layer thickness; friction; damage; static and cyclic friction

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the dynamic and quick development of the automotive and aerospace industries, in mechanical parts (motors, assembly elements, struts, turbine rotor, etc.) or complex tools (carbon fiber draping mold for the manufacture of aircraft doors, etc.) increasing demands, such as safety, reliability, performance, weight reduction, sustainable process, cannot be met by traditional materials, especially when the system is submitted to high mechanical, thermal, and chemical solicitation [1-4]. Aluminum alloys can be a suitable alternative to the materials supporting different types of in-service load [5-7]. They are manufactured in 8 series with hundreds of different specific chemical compositions [8]. The coating of aluminum and its alloys are widely used for its quality of finish and its applications are expanding in various fields, particularly in the transport sector. In the case of anodized aluminum alloys, the damage modes of the layer are mostly in their appearance, source, and category according to the stage of production, but also to the choice of the elaboration parameters [9, 10]. Most damage modes are surface (corrosion, streaking defect, non-uniform appearance, deterioration defects), mechanical (damage due to tensile and bending stress), and

tribological (wear and scratch, fatigue) failure modes [11-16]. The alumina layer which is obtained generally by applying an electrical current and immersing the piece in acid solution is the first body exposed to the tribological damage when the material is solicited in friction [17]. The most widely used high strength aluminum alloys in the aerospace and automotive industries are the 2000 series. However, the main additive component in this alloy, namely the copper, disrupts the formation of the anodic layer and destroys the wear resistance [18-20]. The thickness of the oxide layer is of the order of a few microns. The morphology of this layer comprises a thin barrier layer at the oxide/substrate interface and a thicker porous layer to the outside [18]. Reliable and safe performance of aluminum parts requires a sufficiently accurate assessment of the durability of the alloys. The value of the coefficient of friction and the stability and wear mechanisms are the most important properties for evaluating the friction performance of materials. Many researchers have used tribological tests, such as cyclic resistance tests, to demonstrate the abrasion resistance of anodized aluminum and to examine wear properties and the friction coefficient. Authors in [21] studied the effect of the residual stress on the friction and wear properties has been analyzed. Authors in [20] reported that increasing the thickness

of the anodic coating increased both the compressive strength and the elastic modulus of AA3003 aluminum micro lattice. When studying the tribological properties of the anodic coatings by the dry friction test, authors in [23] noticed that the addition of Al_2O_3 and PTFE particles to the sulfuric-oxalic acid electrolyte resulted in hard anodic composite coatings with improved wear resistance. The results reported in [24] revealed that there was an optimum value for the electrolyte concentration, as well as the hard anodizing current density and the time at which the hardest coating was obtained for the anodized 6061-T6 series. Authors in [9] studied the AA5052 series immersed for 20 min in sulfuric acid solution. The results showed that their morphological and mechanical properties synergistically influenced the damage resistance. The interactions between the released supports and the porous surface changed and the released particles only had a lubricating effect, lowering the coefficient of friction and the wear rate. Authors in [25, 26] studied the effect of anodizing parameters of aluminum alloy EN AW-5251 on the thickness and roughness of Al_2O_3 layers as well as their wettability and tribological properties in sliding combination with the T7W material. The results showed that the anodizing parameters significantly affect the thickness of Al_2O_3 layers. The correlation analysis showed a significant relationship between the roughness parameters and the wettability of the surface of the layers, which affects the ability to create and maintain a sliding film.

Despite the number of studies regarding several parameters which can affect the friction behavior of the anodizing coating, very limited work has been conducted on the effect of anodizing parameters on the tribological failure under static and cyclic friction solicitation of the 2017A T4 aluminum alloys. In fact, in the majority of mechanical parts, the surface of anodized aluminum should resist to static friction (continue, intermittent, discontinue sliding), but also to cyclic loading such as reciprocating sliding, circular sliding, which can help designers in the choice of the suitable characteristics to assume the performance of the material in service. This study investigates the friction behavior of the anodized 2017A aluminum alloy for different conditions of anodization, in terms of coefficient of friction and scratch resistance. The effect of different anodizing parameters related to the applied current and anodizing duration on the tribological behavior of the material is highlighted both under static and cyclic loading. Observations are used to characterize the worn surface and to correlate the friction behavior to the wear mechanisms.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Material

The investigated material is the 2017A-T4 aluminum alloy. The chemical composition of the anodized alloy is shown in Table I. All specimens (50 mm × 30 mm × 3 mm) were individually anodized. Table II shows the established anodizing parameters. Prior to anodizing, the specimens were subjected to different stages of surface preparation to eliminate the spontaneously formed layers:

- Mechanical polishing of grade P120 up to P1500. The objective is to have a smooth surface with low roughness in order to guarantee better surface quality.
- Rinsing with tap water to remove particles adhering to the surface from mechanical polishing.
- Degreasing to clean residual lubricant samples, grease, abrasive grains, and burrs. Degreasing provides a hydrophobic, stain-repellent surface.
- Pickling to eliminate the oxide layer obtained spontaneously on the surface. The pickling bath contains 60 g/l NaOH solution. The sample is immersed in the NaOH bath for 1 min at 60 °C.
- Bleaching to eliminate the blackening of aluminum by aluminum hydroxide. The sample is immersed in a solution of nitric acid (HNO_3) with a concentration of 200 g/l, at room temperature for 2 min.
- Electrochemical polishing to eliminate micro scratches and submicroscopic roughness from the alloy surface. The electro-polishing bath contains acetic acid ((CH_3COOH) 100%: 655 ml/l) and perchloric acid ($(HClO_4)$ 60%: 345 ml/l) at 20 °C. The treatment time is 2 min by applying a voltage of 10 V. The anodizing bath contains diluted sulfuric acid with agitation. A DC stabilizing generator is used to provide the anodizing current.

The experimental parameters i.e. applied current density, sulfuric acid concentration, and duration of anodization are listed in Table II. Three alloy samples were anodized in each experiment.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE ALUMINIUM ALLOY 2017AT4

Element	Wt%
Si	0.66
Fe	0.40
Cu	4.3
Mn	0.6
Mg	0.74
Cr	0.04
Zn	0.19
Ti	0.05
Ti+Zr	0.06
Al	Rest

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS

#	Duration of anodization (min)	Sulfuric acid concentration (g/l)	Applied current density (A/dm^2)	Anodizing bath temperature (°C)
1	30	100	1	15
2	60	100	2	15
3	30	200	2	15

B. Characterization Methods

1) Control of the Thickness of the Oxide Layer

Thickness control of the oxide layer was measured by the eddy current method (coating thickness gauge LPTOSKOP 2042). The principle is to apply a probe on the ideally clean,

flat, and low roughness surface of the coating to be measured. The value range of the thickness is a few micrometers.

2) Scratch Test

For the scratch machine, an indenter, of specific shape and hard material, moves with a constant speed on the surface of the sample by applying a constant normal force during the test. The scratch test was carried out dry on all the samples anodized by the different parameters presented in Table II, applying a load of 6.5 N for a scratch length of 20 mm with a speed of 105 mm/min. The shape of the indenter is conical with an angle of attack equal to 60° .

3) Cyclic Friction Test

The cyclic friction test was carried out under dry conditions in an ambient laboratory environment ($25\text{-}27^\circ\text{C}$) at a Relative Humidity (RH) of 63-67%. Stable sliding motions were applied with a speed of 10 mm/s with a stroke of 15 mm for up to 100 cycles. Friction tests were performed with applied load of 6.5 N and were carried out by a hard steel ball 100Cr6 at dry sliding.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Topographical Analysis of the Coated Surface

Figure 1 shows the surface topography of the anodized surfaces for 30 and 60 min. It is clear that the surface is covered by well distributed oxides with more concentrated and accumulated particles for the 60 min sample. In fact, SEM observation of the surface of the samples shows non-homogeneous surfaces, with microcavities and individualized particles, but agglomerated and randomly distributed. Going from 30 to 60 min, the submicron-sized microcavities slightly increase in size. Their homogeneity improves by increasing the anodizing duration.

Fig. 1. Surface topography of the anodized aluminum alloys for: (a) 30 min and (b) 60 min anodization duration.

B. Influence of Anodizing Duration on the Thickness of the Oxide Layer

A typical in depth microstructure is a network of fine channels created from each discharge event [9]. The oxide coating generally consists of three layers: a barrier layer, an intermediate layer, and an outer layer. After the measurements made by the eddy current method, two ranges of measurements of the thickness of the oxide layer were distinguished. The illustration of the thickness for the 2 materials is given in Figure 2. For the sample 1 of the first experiment with 30 min immersion in the anodizing bath, a thickness of $9.5 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ of the oxide layer was found (Table III). On the other hand, concerning the sample 2 of the second experiment, the thickness of the oxide layer is equal to $12 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$. However, other authors have shown that the surface roughness and the surface curvature have an influence on the value of the thickness of the oxide layer. Also, the contact pressure affects the measurement by the eddy current method [27].

TABLE III. AVERAGE THICKNESS FOR DIFFERENT ANODIZING PARAMETERS

No samples/duration	Sample 1/ 30 min	Sample 2/ 60 min
Average thickness (μm)	9.5	12

Fig. 2. Illustration of the thickness of the oxide layer for: (a) 30 min, (b) 60 min anodizing duration.

Authors in [28] studied the influence of anodizing time on the thickness of the oxide layer and its morphology using replica electron micrographs. They found that the diameter of the pores obtained by the sulfuric anodizing at the surface increases with anodizing time due to the dissolution by sulfuric acid. The increase in the anodizing time causes the growth of the thickness of the oxide layer which becomes a porous layer having a duplex structure consisting of a compact inner layer called barrier layer and a porous outer layer called honeycomb. This porosity is obtained by the chemical dissolution of the oxide layer over time which causes the increase of pore diameters.

C. Influence of the Thickness of the Oxide Layer on the Coefficient of Friction

Figure 3 shows the coefficient of friction (μ) of a sample with $9.5 \mu\text{m}$ thickness measured with the scratch test. To confirm the obtained value of the coefficient of friction, two scratch tests were conducted. The obtained value is of the order of 0.3 and 0.35. Figure 4 shows the coefficient of friction of sample 2 with $12 \mu\text{m}$ thickness. The values obtained by the scratch test range between 0.5 and 0.55. From these values, it is

found that the increase in the anodizing time allows getting a higher μ . Therefore, it can be concluded, that the thickness of the oxide layer influences the coefficient of friction of the oxide layer obtained by the scratch test. The increase in the coefficient of friction is due to the increase in the pore diameter of the oxide layer. Authors in [29] carried out an immersion magnification treatment of anodized samples under different durations and they found that a long anodizing duration has a great impact on the friction level. Authors in [30] carried out wear tests and showed that the variation of the coefficient of friction depends on the morphology of the oxide layer. They reported that the coefficient of friction tends to increase with increasing pore size.

Fig. 3. Coefficient of friction for sample 1.

Fig. 4. Coefficient of friction for sample 2.

D. Influence of the Applied Current on the Tribological Behavior of the Oxide Layer

The main role of the current applied during anodizing treatment is to increase the reaction speed in order to ensure the movement of the electrons between the anode and the cathode in the electrolyte bath. The variation of the applied current has an important influence on the tribological properties of the oxide layer. In our case, two applied currents of anodizing treatment were studied and the wear resistance of the alumina layer was analyzed. Figure 5 presents the evolution of the friction coefficient of sample 1. The average friction coefficient of the specimen of 1 A/dm^2 applied current is 0.55. The frictional response throughout the tribological characterization test. Furthermore, according to Figure 6, showing the SEM observations of the friction scar of the sample 1 with different magnifications, the oxide layer is completely removed, which

confirms the result of Figure 5. The cyclic friction test induces the formation of the wear particles which is composed of the alloy of aluminum and the alumina layer. In addition, the wear fragment is compacted on the surface of the substrate (Figure 6(b)).

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the coefficient of friction of the sample 2 with a variation of the applied current density from 1 A/dm^2 to 2 A/dm^2 . Sample 2 has a low friction coefficient of the order of 0.3 for the first 30 cycles. Then it gradually increases with a slight slope to reach a value of 0.8 before stabilizing after 75 cycles. Hence, it is clear that the wear resistance of the oxide layer varies with the applied current, as it is greater for an applied current density of 2 A/dm^2 than for 1 A/dm^2 . Figure 8 displays the SEM observations with different magnifications. These images show that there is a partial detachment of the oxide layer (Figure 8(a)) from the substrate with the formation of the micrometric wear particles of varying sizes (Figure 8(c)). The wear debris is compacted on the surface, forming a smoother scar that fills the porosity of the oxide layer. In addition, vertical cracks perpendicular to the direction of friction appear at the wear scar (Figure 8(b)). The compacted wear particle is responsible for the increments of the friction coefficient after 30 cycles since the surface becomes smooth.

Fig. 5. Evolution of the friction response under cyclic test- sample 1.

Fig. 6. (a) Post process analysis of sample 1: (a) $1 \text{ A/dm}^2 + 100 \text{ g/l}$, (b) corresponding detail of the framed zone of (a).

When they studied the effect of reaction time on the cyclic behavior of the 5083 aluminum alloy oxide layer, authors in [31] reported that increasing the RT improved the durability of the material. In addition, when RT increased, the stability of the friction coefficient was improved and the pores on the surface were further filled with micro-sized wear particles, inducing the establishment of a compacted layer. Therefore, the 5083 aluminum alloy oxide layer shows a similar behavior to the reference 2017A T4, and has important tribological characteristics such as durability and wear resistance after hundreds of friction cycles. Authors in [29, 30] found that the variation of the friction coefficient depends on the morphology of the oxide layer and that this coefficient tends to increase with increasing pore size.

Fig. 7. Evolution of the friction response using cyclic friction test of sample 2.

Fig. 8. SEM image of the wear mechanisms obtained by the cyclic friction test for the sample 2: (a) 2 A/dm². (b), (c) higher magnification images of (a).

E. Influence of the Applied Current and the Electrolyte Concentration on the Tribological Behavior of the Oxide Layer

A simultaneous increase in the applied current and concentration was studied in sample 3. Figure 9 shows the friction response of the fourth cyclic friction test with an

increase of the concentration from 100 g/l to 200 g/l and a variation of the applied current density from 1 A/dm² to 2 A/dm². The high conductivity coupled with the acceleration of the anodizing reaction gives the most stable response with a low friction coefficient. The obtained friction coefficient is of the order of 0.34. This value is very close to that of the first 30 cycles of the friction test of sample 2. The SEM microscope observation of the damage morphology with different magnifications (Figure 10) shows that during the cyclic friction test the oxide layer stands 100 cycles. Indeed, the alumina layer does not wear off and there is no penetration of the substrate (Figure 10(b)). At higher magnification (Figure 10(c)), vertical and horizontal fatigue cracks appear in the wear scar, which explains the great hardness of the anodized surface. This finding confirms the good stability and the value of the friction coefficient. Therefore, after the comparative study performed in this article, the last sample has a high resistance to abrasion and wear.

Fig. 9. Curve of the friction response using cyclic friction test of sample 3.

Fig. 10. SEM images of the wear mechanisms obtained by the cyclic friction test for the sample 3: (a) 2 A/dm², (b)-(c) higher magnification images of (a).

IV. CONCLUSION

The friction behavior of the aluminum alloy 2017A was studied on relation to the effect of anodic oxide layer thickness which is controlled by the anodizing potential. Two durations of anodization, 30 and 60 min, were particularly examined. Based on the present experiments, the following conclusions are drawn:

- The variation of the anodizing duration has a marked effect on the thickness of the oxide layer.
- Longer anodizing duration yielded thicker and harder aluminum oxide coating.
- The increase in the thickness of the anodic oxide layer increases the coefficient of friction.
- Variations in coefficient of friction with sliding distance are influenced by changes in wear morphology and degree of oxidation. The treated surfaces with a thickness of 50 μm have the lowest friction coefficients and wear rates. Their improved wear resistance may be related to the increased bond strength compared to other anodized surfaces.
- The tribological damage was characterized by the detachment of debris, which increases with the increase of the duration of anodization. Upon sliding, its detachment leads to delamination of the underlying anodic aluminum oxides and subsequent abrasion of the aluminum substrate.

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Word Sense Disambiguation applied to Assamese-Hindi Bilingual Statistical Machine Translation

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ABSTRACT

Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) is concerned with automatically assigning the appropriate sense to an ambiguous word. WSD is an important task and plays a crucial role in many Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications. A Statistical Machine Translation (SMT) system translates a source into a target language based on phrase-based statistical translation. MT plays a crucial role in a WSD system, as a source language word may be associated with multiple translations in the target language. This study aims to apply WSD to the input of the MT system to enhance the disambiguation output. Hindi WordNet was used by selecting the most frequent synonym to obtain the most accurate translation. This study also compared Naïve Bayes (NB) and Decision Tree (DT) to test and build a WSD model. NB was more appropriate for the WSD task than DT when evaluated in the Weka machine learning toolkit. To the best of our knowledge, no such work has been carried out yet for the Assamese Indo-Aryan language. The applied WSD achieved better results than the baseline MT system without embedding the WSD module. The results were analyzed by linguist scholars. Furthermore, the Assamese-Hindi transliteration system was merged with the baseline MT system for the translation of proper nouns. This study marks a remarkable contribution to Assamese NLP, which is a low computationally aware Indian language.

Keywords-word sense disambiguation; machine translation; machine learning; assamese; natural language processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Any natural language contains words that have different meanings when used in various contexts. These words are termed ambiguous words, and Word Sense Disambiguation (SWD) is used to resolve lexical ambiguities based on the context. Ambiguity occurs in various NLP phases, such as lexical, syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and discourse levels [1]. This study aims to disambiguate lexical semantic ambiguities, such as:

- সীতা এজনী কলা/artপেমী ছোৱালী (*Sita is an artistic girl*)
- ছোৱালীজনী জন্মে পৰা কলা/deaf sense (*The girl is deaf from her birth*).

Both of the above sentences are syntactically correct but the semantics or meaning of the lexicon "কলা"/kola are different in both sentences. WSD is initialized with the following main requirements: sense repository, document representation, and approach identification [2]. Many supervised, unsupervised, and semi-supervised learning approaches are adopted,

considering a machine-readable dictionary as a sense repository and representing the document with important features for the WSD task. Machine Learning (ML) approaches are widely used for sense classification tasks. Supervised WSD approaches use a large number of algorithms and achieve high accuracies [3]. The algorithms are trained on sense-annotated datasets and are tested on some unseen events. This study adopted supervised ML approaches, Naïve Bayes (NB) and Decision Tree (DT), for a word sense disambiguation task. The NB and DT algorithms were also used in [4-5] for word sense disambiguation tasks. A comparative analysis was performed on DT and NB, and since NB had a lower error rate than DT, the NB classifier was used for the proposed WSD method.

A Machine Translation (MT) system automatically translates a source into a target language. The rapidly increasing rate of digitalized documents requires an automatic MT system, as every human wants to retrieve information in an understandable language. Rule-based, statistical, and hybrid approaches are used to develop automated MT systems. Statistical translation systems, such as Moses, allow any language pair to develop automatic translation models. This study chose a statistical approach for the Assamese-Hindi MT system, which required training of several bilingual parameters in both the source and target languages.

Assamese is the official language of the northeastern state of India, Assam. It is spoken by nearly 13-14 million people. Assam shares an international border with Bhutan and Bangladesh. It additionally shares a culture and climate similar to Southeast Asia. It is a computationally less aware language that belongs to the Indo-Aryan language family. Recently, some developments have been made for this Assamese language from a technological perspective. Information Retrieval (IR), Assamese WordNet, and Corpus [5], which are important resources for Assamese NLP, were developed. Assamese WordNet was framed in [6]. Based on Hindi WordNet [7], the Assamese WordNet structure was developed by lexicographers as part of the Indo-WordNet project. WordNet is a combination of four main components: ID, CAT, SYNSETS, and GLOSS. ID is the unique identification number, CAT indicates the category or parts of speech, SYNSET is the basic building block of WordNet, which has a vector of synonymous words, and GLOSS defines the meaning.

In [8], a combination of statistical approaches and a WordNet-based SMT system was investigated [8]. This study used Assamese WordNet to retrieve the most appropriate translated word in the English-Assamese SMT system. This lexical resource has not been used in any other study of the Assamese language. Furthermore, the Assamese-English transliteration system was combined with the baseline system for proper nouns and achieved acceptable accuracy when analyzed by linguistic scholars. In [9], another SMT system was presented for Assamese to Bengali. Both Assamese and Bengali share the same code letters, the only difference being the symbolic representation of the letter 'ৱ' (Assamese letter Ra) and the individual letter 'ঝ' (Assamese letter Khya). The system was tested using the Bi-Lingual Evaluation Understudy (BLEU) score and achieved satisfactory results. This study aims to integrate the WSD module into the baseline Assamese-

Hindi MT system. To our knowledge, no other study has attempted it before in this Indo-Aryan language. Therefore, this study marks a great contribution to Assamese NLP.

II. THE PROPOSED APPROACH

For the WSD task, a table representing the average F-scores of both the NB and DT classifiers is shown when implemented on Weka. The C4.5 DT algorithm and the NB classifier were used to compare, choose, and build an appropriate WSD model. Figure 1 shows the system architecture.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the proposed method.

A. Preparation of Parallel Corpus

Digitized Assamese-Hindi documents are few, so a parallel corpus of Assamese-Hindi was prepared by lexicographers from the GU NLP team. The Assamese-Hindi corpus contains 10K records. Only 3.6K records in the parallel corpus contain ambiguous terms. Some ambiguous terms have only one sense associated with the set of the parallel corpus. Among the 3.6K records, 300 instances were regarded as test data to evaluate the MT system. However, the whole 9.7K data was viewed as train data, as the MT system needs to translate all other words in the input other than the ambiguous term. A hold-out evaluation strategy, splitting the whole dataset into train and test data, was considered to evaluate the MT system. Various preprocessing phases, such as corpus cleaning and removal of junk values and blank spaces, were performed. As the tool was implemented in a Linux environment, the encoding of the parallel files was converted from Windows to Linux. It was also verified whether the source language in the parallel file was aligned with the same translated target lines or not.

B. Developing the Language Model

Given a string of words $W = w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$, $P(w)$ according to Markov chain is given by:

$$P(w) = P(w_1)P(w_2|w_1)P(w_3|w_2)P(w_4|w_3)P(w_n|w_{n-1})$$

This computation is for a 2-gram language model. The maximum likelihood estimation is given by:

$$P(w_2|w_1) = \text{count}(w_1, w_2) / \text{count}(w_1)$$

Thus, a language model gives the probability of a sentence using the n -gram model. SRILM is a toolkit for building statistical language models, primarily for use in statistical tagging. This tool has been in development by the SRI Speech Technology and Research Laboratory since 1995. SRILM consists mainly of a set of C++ class libraries that implement language models, supporting data structures, and some utility functions [10]. This study used the SRILM toolkit to develop a language model for the Hindi corpus. The command executed in the Linux terminal was:

```
/media/sandhan/1214a349-753f-4189-83ed-1024026066ae/home/salma/poses/srilm-1.7.1/bin/i686-gcc4/ngram-count -order 3 -interpolate discount -unk-text ../corpus/train.clean.hi -lm surfl1.lm;
```

C. Developing the Translation Model

This model helps to count the conditional probabilities of source and target language training pairs by the formula $P(S/T)$. The computation was carried out by breaking the sentence into words or phrases and their probabilities were mastered. GIZA-PP [11] is a statistical MT toolkit that is used to train word classes using maximum-likelihood criteria. This generates a mooses.ini file in the /model directory [12]:

```
/media/sandhan/1214a349-753f-4189-83ed-1024026066ae/home/salma/poses/mosesdecoder/scripts/training/train-model.perl/media/sandhan/1214a349-753f-4189-83ed1024026066ae/home/salma/poses/mosesdecoder/corpus/--corpus train.clean --e hi --f ass --lm0:3:/media/sandhan/1214a349-753f-4189-83ed1024026066ae/home/salma/poses/mosesdecoder/languageasshi/surfl1.lm:0 -reordering distance,msd- bidirectional-fe -external-bin-dir /media/sandhan/1214a349-753f-4189-83ed1024026066ae/home/salma/poses/mosesdecoder/tools;
```

D. Baseline SMT System using the Moses Decoder

This phase of SMT maximizes the probability of translated text corresponding to the source text. The target word/phrase is selected if it maximizes the following formula:

$$P(S|T) = \operatorname{argmax} P(T)P(S|T)$$

Inputting the following command in the terminal, the output was:

```
echo "গৰম আৰু শীতকালত" ./moses-f
../working/ashi/model/moses.ini
```

TABLE I. OUTPUT OF BASELINE TRANSLATION

SI no	Assamese sentences	English Translation	Hindi sentences
1	ইয়াত চৰাই আৰু জন্তু আছে (Iyat sorai aru jantu ase)	Here there are birds and animals	यहां पक्षी और जानवर है
2	আৰব এজন কলা ল'ৰা হয় (Aarab ajon kola lora hoi)	Aarab is a deaf boy	अरब एक बहरा लड़का है
3	তাজ মহোৎসৱ ভাৰতত হয় (Taj mahotsav bharatohoi)	Taj festival is held in India	ताज महोत्सव भारत है
4	জামু পাহাৰৰ ওপৰত (Jammu paharor uporot)	Jammu is in the hills	जम्मू पहाड़ी के ऊपर
5	নৃত্য এটা কলা হয় (Nitya eta kola hoi)	Dance is an art	नृत्य एक कला है

Fig. 2. Baseline translation output.

E. Assamese-Hindi Transliteration System

For the proper nouns, such as the one in the above table in Assamese sentence (2), আৰব/aarab was translated to আৰব by SMT. Thus, a list of parallel proper nouns (Assamese-Hindi) was prepared. Several named entities were prepared and translated by linguistic scholars, helping to some extent in the translation of Out-Of-Vocabulary (OOV) words. A look-up-based approach was used for the transliteration task.

TABLE II. OUTPUT OF TRANSLITERATION SYSTEM

S/N	Assamese sentences	Hindi sentences
1	ইয়াত চৰাই আৰু জন্তু আছে (Iyat sorai aru jantu ase)	यहां पक्षी और जानवर है
2	আৰব এজন কলা ল'ৰা হয় (Aarab ajon kola lora hoi)	अरब एक बहरा लड़का है
3	তাজ মহোৎসৱ ভাৰতত হয় (Taj mahotsav bharatohoi)	ताज महोत्सव भारत है
4	জামু পাহাৰৰ ওপৰত (Jammu paharor uporot)	जम्मू पहाड़ी के ऊपर
5	নৃত্য এটা কলা হয় (Nitya eta kola hoi)	नृत्य एक बहरा है

F. WSD and WordNet Embedded System

1) Comparative Analysis between NB and C4.5 DT to Build the WSD Model

The sense inventory was prepared by extracting ambiguous terms from both Assamese WordNet and Corpus. The number of unique ambiguous words in the sense inventory was 110, of which 50 (from 15K words from Assamese WordNet) and 60 (18K unique words from Assamese Corpus when mapped to 50K sentences) are derived to date. The senses/meanings were manually put in the database by the lexicographers for the ambiguous words derived from the Assamese corpus. The size of Assamese sense-tagged data was 4K, based on the sense inventory and considering unordered semantic features $\{-3, -2, -1, +1, +2, +3\}$. In supervised approaches, it is common to have high dimensional data, but sometimes it is difficult to collect large datasets or examples to represent each pattern or object class of an ambiguous word. The same is the case for the Assamese language. Data containing ambiguous terms of different senses were collected from digitalized content of Assamese Corpus and crawled data from a set of Assamese websites using Nutch1.4. The test involved ten different ambiguous words with 50 instances each of ambiguous words, and the dataset was unbalanced. The comparative experiments were carried out in the Weka ML toolkit. Table V shows the results of the average F-scores of seven ambiguous words. K-fold cross-validation ($k = 10$) was used, as the sense-tagged data was small. The NB classifier had a lower error rate than

DT. The low performance of DT for the WSD task can be attributed to overfitting. A model is efficient when it not only fits the training data well but also knows how to classify the test instances that it has not seen in the previous records. When a DT is fully grown, it loses generalization ability, which is known as the overfitting problem. There are various causes of the overfitting problem of DTs. One problem found is the lack of representative instances. The following example demonstrates the problem [13-14].

TABLE III. SAMPLE SHOWING THE OVERFITTING PROBLEM OF DT

Name	Body_Temperature	Gives_Birth	Four_Legged	Hibernates	Class_label
Salamander	Cold_blood	No	Yes	Yes	No
Guppy	Cold_blood	Yes	No	No	No
Eagle	Warm_blood	No	No	No	No
Poorwill	Warm_blood	No	No	Yes	No
Platypus	Warm_blood	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Fig. 3. Decision Tree (DT).

In Figure 3, the terminal nodes denote: Yes (Y): Mammals, and No (N): Non-mammals. Now, consider some test instances or tuples as given in Table IV.

TABLE IV. TEST SAMPLES ON THE DT FORMED

Name	Body_Temperature	Gives_Birth	Four_legged	Hibernates	Class_label
Human	Warm_blood	Yes	No	No	Yes
Anteatar	Warm_blood	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Elephant	Warm_blood	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Dolphin	Warm_blood	Yes	No	No	Yes
Platypus	Warm_blood	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

Among the testing instances, only Anteatar was classified correctly and Human, Elephant, and Dolphin were misclassified by the DT. This is because of a lack of training samples. There is only one tuple (Eagle) with such characteristics.

2) Naïve Bayes (NB) Chosen for the Disambiguation Task

NB was used to disambiguate the ambiguous terms in the input language. The Assamese sense tagged data (4K size) with the sense inventory of Assamese WordNet & Corpus was considered. A hold-out evaluation strategy was used for the disambiguation task. A search technique was applied to determine if the input language contains ambiguous terms by a

look-up-based approach in the sense inventory. If any ambiguous term is detected, then the term is tagged with its corresponding sense by the NB classifier. Manual intervention was required to check if the appropriate sense was associated with the ambiguous term. Verified by the validators, the sense was later mapped to Hindi WordNet [14-18]. It should be noted that if the sense associated is from the sense inventory Assamese WordNet, then it can be mapped to Hindi WordNet. However, if the unique ambiguous terms with their senses are defined from Assamese Corpus, they cannot be mapped to Hindi WordNet as no such ambiguous words are available in Assamese WordNet. For example, consider an input sentence "নৃত্য এটা কলা হয়" (Nitya eta kola hoi). In the Assamese language, the word "কলা/kola" is ambiguous. The NB classifier recognizes the ambiguous word using the sense inventory and assigns the appropriate sense based on the learned sense-tagged module [15-16]. On verifying the sense tagged to the ambiguous term, it was found that the term "কলা/kola" has two distinct senses, as shown from the Assamese WordNet sense inventory in Table VI. A sample of Assamese sense-tagged data is shown below for the ambiguous word "আদি/aadi":

- @relation aadi
- @attribute text string
- @attribute sense {ইত্যাদি-etc-30, মূল-root-20}
- @data
- "মাউচ কিবৰ্ড আদি কম্পিউটাৰ আহিলা", ইত্যাদি, etc. ("Mouse Keyboard aadi computer ahila", ityadi)
- "হৰিণা গঁড় মহ আদি জন্তু আছ", ইত্যাদি, etc. ("Harina Garh moh aadi jantu ase", ityadi)
- "কামাখ্যা উমানন্দ বিশিষ্ট আদি কামৰূপৰ তীৰ্থস্থান", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Kamakhya Umanda Basistha aadi Kamrupor tirthosthan, ityadi)
- "দোকানখন সাধুকথা ব্যঙ্গচিত্ৰ আদি পোৱা যায়", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Dokankhon hadhukotha byngachitra aadi powa jai, ityadi)
- "বুৰঞ্জী জ্যোতিষতত্ত্ব সাঁথৰ আদি প্ৰকাশিত হৈছিল ভাৰতীয়", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Buranji jyotikhtatba hathor aadi prokakhit hoisil bharatiya, ityadi)
- "মাইনা অৰুণ সৰিভ আদি কাকত আলোচনী প্ৰকাশেও", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Moina Arun Surabhi aadi kakot alosoni prokasheo, ityadi)
- "বিহীয়া মিচিং কাৰ্বি আদি জনজাতীয় নৃত্য প্ৰেৰণ", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Bihiya Missing Karbi aadi janajatiya nritya jathesta, ityadi)
- "নাদ খন্দা আদি বিভিন্ন ধৰণ কাম", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Nad khanda aadi bibhinna dharan kam, ityadi)
- "জেং বিহু হুচৰি আদি ৰঙালি বিহুৰ লগত", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Jeng bihu husari aadi rangali bihur logat)
- "খাৰু জোনবিৰি বঢ়হমথুৰি আদি নাচনিয়ে বিহুত বঢ়হাৰ", ইত্যাদি, etc. (Kharu jonbiri borhamuthuri aadi nasoniye bihut byabahaar, ityadi)

- "মানস চৈখোৱা ওৰাং আদি অসম ৰাষ্ট্ৰীয় উদ্যান", ইত্যাদি, etc. (*Manas Saikhowa Orang aadi asom ratriya uddan, ityadi*)
- "বাল্মিকী আদিতে দস্যু আছিল", মল root (*Balmiki adite dashyu asil, mul*)
- "কালিদাস আদিতে অকৰা আছিল", মল root (*Kalidas adite okora asil, mul*)
- "ৰংঘ আদিতে কাঠ অট্টালিকা আছিল", মল root (*Rangha adite kath attalika asil, mul*)
- "শুনাৰায় তাজমহল আদিতে শিৱ মন্দিৰ আছিল", মল root (*Hunajai Tajmahal adite shiv mandir asil, mul*).

TABLE V. STATISTICS OF SENSE-TAGGED DATA

Dataset	Collected Total sense_tagged instances	Number of senses of each ambiguous word	Type of evaluation	Average F-score of NB	Average F-score of DT
7 highly Assamese ambiguous words	350	Binary	10 fold cross validation	0.83	0.75

TABLE VI. SAMPLE OF ASSAMESE AND HINDI WORDNET

Assamese WordNet	Hindi WordNet
SynsetID : 1642 Synonyms : কলা, আৰ্ট, Gloss : কোনো কাম ভালকৈ কৌশল, বিশেষকৈ এনেকুৱা কাম প্ৰাকসম্পাদন কৰিবলৈ জ্ঞানৰ উপৰি কৌশল আৰু অভ্যাসৰ আৱশ্যক হয় SynsetID : 7196	SynsetID : 1642 Synonyms : कला, फन, ফন, ছনৰ, বদ্বিয়া
Synonyms : কলা, বধিৰ, শ্ৰুতিহীন, শ্ৰুতিশক্তিহীন, শ্ৰৱণৰহিত, শ্ৰৱণশক্তিৰহিত, শ্ৰুতিৰহিত, কাণ_গধুৰ, Gloss : পিাজনে শুনা নাপায়	SynsetID : 7196 Synonyms : बहुरा, बधरि, বহুৱা, বধৰি, উচুৰৈশ্বৰা, স্বীৰহীন

TABLE VII. OUTPUT OF EMBEDDED BASELINE SMT WITH WSD AND TRANSLITERATION SYSTEM

	Assamese sentences	Hindi Sentences
1	ইয়াত চৰাই আৰু জন্তু আছে (<i>Iyat sorai aru jantu ase</i>)	যহা পক্ষী আৰু জানৱৰ হৈ
2	আৰব এজন কলা লৰা হয় (<i>Aarab ajon kola lora hoi</i>)	অৰব এক বহুৱা লড়কা হৈ
3	তাজ মহোৎসৱ ভাৰতত হয় (<i>Taj mahotsav bharatohoi</i>)	তাজ মহোৎসৱ ভাৰতত হৈ
4	জামু পাহাৰৰ ওপৰত (<i>Jammu paharor uporot</i>)	জম্মু পাহাৰী ক উপৰ
5	নৃত্য এটা কলা হয় (<i>Nitya eta kola hoi</i>)	নৃত্য এক কলা হৈ

The baseline SMT system Assamese-Hindi source word "কলা" is translated to the target word "বহুৱা", which is a wrong output of the MT system. So, a disambiguation task is performed on the input before passing it to the MT system to get correctly translated. The disambiguation performed by the NB classifier "কলা" was sense tagged with sense id 1642. After this, it was mapped with the same sense id of the Hindi WordNet, which is the most frequent synonym of id 1642 "কলা" of Hindi WordNet. The WordNet's most frequent synonym was embedded to get the perfect translated Hindi

word. Now, the input to the SMT was "নৃত্য এটা কলা হয়" (*Nitya eta kola hoi*) and the correct MT system output form "নৃত্য এক কলা হৈ" was obtained. More such words have different Hindi translations, as shown in Table VIII, and some have the same translation even if used in different senses in different contexts, as shown in Table IX.

TABLE VIII. DIFFERENT ASSAMESE-HINDI TRANSLATIONS WITH DIFFERENT SENSES

Assamese ambiguous words	Different Hindi senses with different translated forms
কলা (kal)	उद्योग, कला
আহাৰ (ahar)	आहार, असार
অন্তৰ (antar)	दलि, अंतर
আদি (aadi)	आदि, जड़
কবি (kobi)	गोभी, कवि

TABLE IX. SAME ASSAMESE-HINDI TRANSLATION WITH DIFFERENT SENSES

Assamese ambiguous words	Different Hindi senses with different translated forms
কৰ (kar)	कर
উত্তৰ (uttar)	उत्तर

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system was tested with 300 different Assamese sentences that contained ambiguous words. The whole output sample is shown in phases through the tables above. Table I is the sample output of the baseline SMT Assamese-Hindi system. Here, the proper nouns "আৰব" and "জাম" were not translated into Hindi and were the same on the output line. Moreover, the baseline system incorrectly translated the ambiguous word "কলা" in sentence 5 to "বহুৱা". In sentence 3 of Table I, "তাজ মহোৎসৱ ভাৰতত" was properly translated to "তাজ মহোৎসৱ ভাৰতত", as these OOV words may be trained by the MT system, but "মহোৎসৱ" was not. The baseline system in the next phase was combined with a transliteration system for out-of-vocabulary words. Here, the proper nouns "আৰব" and "জাম" were correctly transliterated to "অৰব" and "জম্ম", as shown in Table II. In sentence 5 of Table I, the output was not yet correct, so the WSD system was applied to help the baseline SMT system output correct the translated form. After associating the appropriate sense with the WSD module, the system was optimized with a large lexical resource, Hindi WordNet. WordNet provides the most frequent synonym of the same synset id in the sense denoted by the NB classifier. The translated output shown in Table VII was correct when a combination of the WSD module and Hindi WordNet was embedded into the baseline MT and transliteration system. Tables VIII and IX depict certain Assamese ambiguous words that have different translated forms and the same word form corresponding to their respective senses. The sentences tested achieved 76-77% accuracy. A bilingual Assamese-Hindi parallel corpus containing ambiguous terms can further increase the accuracy.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study embedded WSD to obtain the correct translation output from the SMT system. WSD is an important task in

many NLP applications. When embedding the WSD module into the baseline MT system, a significant improvement was observed in the output. At first, a statistical baseline MT system using Moses and OOV words was combined in the baseline with the transliteration system. Certain words have different meanings from different Hindi-translated words. At first, the ambiguous words were disambiguated in the appropriate sense using the NB classifier and the proper and most frequent synonym from Hindi WordNet before being passed to the SMT module. This improves the output result to a correct translated Assamese-Hindi form. The system was tested, and the results were analyzed by linguist scholars. More parallel and sense-tagged trained data comprising ambiguous terms with different senses, transliterated forms, and high-accuracy WSD models will enable the MT system to achieve even higher accuracy.

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Discharge Coefficient of a Two-Rectangle Compound Weir combined with a Semicircular Gate beneath it under Various Hydraulic and Geometric Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Two-component composite hydraulic structures are commonly employed in irrigation systems. The first component, responsible for managing the overflow, is represented by a weir consisting of two rectangles. The second component, responsible for regulating the underflow, is represented by a semicircular gate. Both components are essential for measuring, directing, and controlling the flow. In this study, we experimentally investigated the flow through a combined two-rectangle sharp-crested weir with a semicircular gate placed across the channel as a control structure. The upper rectangle of the weir has a width of 20 cm, while the lower rectangle has varying widths (W_2) of 5, 7, and 9 cm and depths (z) of 6, 9, and 11 cm. Additionally, three different values were considered for the gate diameter (d), namely 8, 12, and 15 cm. These dimensions were tested interchangeably, including a weir without a gate ($d = 0$), under different water head conditions. The results indicate that the discharge passing through the combined structure of the two rectangles and the gate is significantly affected by the weir and gate dimensions. After analyzing the data, empirical formulas were developed to predict the discharge coefficient (C_d) of the combined structure. It is important to note that the analysis and results presented in this study are limited to the range of data that were tested.

Keywords-compound weir; semicircular gates; discharge coefficient; combined structure; open channels; discharge measurement

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydraulic structures such as gates and weirs play a crucial role in regulating the open channels flow. One advantage of using gates on their own is their ability to retain floating materials. However, this potential issue can be avoided by combining gates with weirs. Conversely, when weirs are used exclusively, sedimentation problems may arise, but these can also be addressed by combining weirs and gates [1-4]. The hydraulic behavior of these combined weir and gate structures differs from that of individual weirs or gates. They effectively resolve all the issues that may emerge when weirs and gates operate independently. Numerous studies have been conducted to accurately estimate the discharge coefficient (C_d) in cases of simultaneous flow over the weir and under the gate. Furthermore, authors in [5, 6] investigated the geometrical properties of combined structures under various hydraulic conditions, including weir width (W_2), gate diameter (d), upstream water head, combined structure width, and height.

Authors in [7] presented a governing equation for calculating the discharge over a triangular, sharp-crested weir. Additionally, several empirical equations were formulated to

estimate discharge over various types of weirs [8-10]. Authors in [11] estimated the discharge of the inverted V-shaped gate in a combined system composed of a rectangular weir and a triangular gate using the discharge equation derived in [12]. Their findings indicated that the triangular gate significantly influences the combined discharge. Authors in [13] experimented with rectangular compound sharp-crested side weirs [13]. It was observed that there is no significant correlation between the upstream Froude number and the discharge coefficient. Authors in [14] conducted a comparison between the numerical results obtained from the Flow 3D software and experimental tests to investigate the flow characteristics of a compound system comprising a vertical sharp-crested weir and gate. Authors in [15] examined the flow characteristics over a combined sharp-crowned rectangular-triangular weir. Authors in [16] employed a combined structure consisting of two triangular sections with different notch angles to measure flow rates for a range of discharges. Authors in [17] tested the free flow characteristics through a combination of a triangular weir and a rectangular sluice gate. They concluded that the weir angle exhibited an inverse relationship with the discharge coefficient, which, in turn, displayed a direct

correlation with the vertical distance between the weir and the gate. Authors in [18] studied the flow over a rectangular sharp-crested weir and under an inverted rectangular sharp gate. Their findings revealed that both surface tension and viscosity had a significant impact on the combined discharge. Authors in [19] explored the flow features of a combination of a V-notch weir and a rectangular sluice gate. Authors in [20] conducted experimental runs to investigate the flow dynamics beneath a rectangular sluice gate and over a trapezoidal sharp-crested weir. Their findings indicated that enlarging the gap between the lower edge of the weir and the upper edge of the gate increased the discharge coefficient of the combined structure. Authors in [21] examined the discharge coefficient of a combined structure comprising a rectangular, sharp-crowned weir and a semicircular gate. Authors in [22] studied the combined flow over sharply crested weirs and beneath gates. Authors in [23] conducted experiments on a combined triangular weir and rectangular gate structure to determine its discharge coefficient. Authors in [24] carried out experimental runs on a compound weir consisting of two rectangles separated by sloping sides, along with a circular gate beneath it. Their objective was to develop empirical equations for calculating the combined weir discharge coefficient, considering various geometric and hydraulic properties.

The primary objective of this paper is to determine the discharge coefficient of the given combined structure. Unlike the conventional use of weirs and gates separately, the combined weir and gate structure is a relatively new system that has been proposed by several researchers. The main advantage of this combined system is the reduction of sedimentation and deposition upstream of the system, particularly when it comes to discharge measurement and control of the irrigation channel flow. Integrated weir and gate systems are cost-effective in terms of operation and maintenance, as they are self-cleaning discharge measurement devices. In this study, the hydraulic characteristics of a combined overflow weir and a semicircular gate below were experimentally investigated. Additionally, we explored various dimensions of the weir and gate, including the use of a weir without a gate. This exploration aimed to develop a more precise formula for calculating the discharge coefficient for this type of structure.

II. THEORY

Figure 1 displays the composite structure's perspectives, along with a sketch depicting the concurrent flow over weirs and beneath gates. The subsequent list enumerates the independent variables that can be employed to ascertain the combined discharge, both over weirs and beneath gates:

$$C_d = f(h_1, h_2, h_3, W_1, W_2, d, W, H, Z, \rho, g, \mu, \sigma) \quad (1)$$

where C_d is the discharge coefficient, h_1 is the water head on the upper weir rectangle sill, h_2 is the water head on the lower weir rectangle sill, h_3 is the water head on the semicircular gate upstream of the combined structure, W_1 and W_2 are the upper and lower weir rectangle widths, respectively, Z is depth of the lower rectangle, d is the semicircular gate diameter, H and W are the total height and width of the combined structure, ρ is the

water density, g is the gravitational acceleration, μ is the water dynamic viscosity, and σ is the water surface tension.

Applying Buckingham's π theory and its associated characteristics to (1), we can derive dimensionless groups that influence the concurrent discharge coefficient for the flow over a compound weir with a semicircular gate beneath it.

$$C_d = f\left(\frac{h_1}{H}, \frac{h_2}{H}, \frac{h_3}{H}, \frac{W_1}{W}, \frac{W_2}{W}, \frac{Z}{H}, \frac{d}{H}, R_e, W_e\right) \quad (2)$$

where R_e and W_e represent the Reynolds and Weber numbers, respectively. It is assumed that these numbers have a negligible impact on the combined structure unless the head becomes exceptionally low. It should be noted that the aforementioned nondimensional groups can be combined to generate various dimensionless numbers. Several researchers have explored in literature the relationships between discharge and water depth for gates and weirs. Authors in [25] developed the renowned equation for flow over weirs, which was reformulated using superposition as follows:

$$Q_w = \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{2g} (W_1 - W_2) h_1^{3/2} + \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{2g} W_2 h_2^{3/2} \quad (3)$$

where Q_w is the theoretical discharge passing through the weir.

Also, the discharge through gates was given in [26] as:

$$Q_g = \frac{\pi}{8} d^2 \sqrt{2gh_3} \quad (4)$$

where Q_g is the gate theoretical discharge.

$$Q_{th} = Q_w + Q_g \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{act} = C_d Q_{th} \quad (6)$$

$$Q_{act} = C_d \left(\frac{2}{3} \sqrt{2g} (W_1 - W_2) h_1^{3/2} + \frac{2}{3} \sqrt{2g} W_2 h_2^{3/2} + \frac{\pi}{8} d^2 \sqrt{2gh_3} \right) \quad (7)$$

where C_d is the discharge coefficient of the combined structure.

Fig. 1. Sketch of the compound weir with the semicircular gate positioned below.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experimental runs were carried out to achieve the purpose of this paper using a rectangular flume with dimensions of 4.0

m in length, 0.30 m in width, and 0.50 m in height. The closed water cycle is utilized by the self-contained experimental setup. A three-horsepower pump powers the flume's water-circulating system efficiently. The glassy sheets that make up the flume's side walls accommodate the experimental run observation. Baffle vertical plates were positioned at the entrance of the channel to prevent vortex motion and regulate the flow to control the damp fluctuations at the flume's entry. The exit water from the combined structure was collected into a hydraulic bench F13 type, and the volume of the collected water in the hydraulic bench was divided by the corresponding time to calculate the actual discharge (Figure 2).

Fig. 2. The flume and hydraulic bench layout.

For every experimental run, the actual discharge was determined as the average of three recorded discharge values. A vernier-type gauge with a 1 mm accuracy was used to measure the weir heads, h_1 and h_2 , as well as the semicircular gate head, h_3 . Calibration was performed before every experimental run to avoid instrument errors. The depth rod was precisely adjusted to the water's surface in order to guarantee that the channel's flow remained steady and constant. Throughout each experimental run, the discharge maintained constant. Rectangular sharp compound weir with a lower semicircular gate was made of acrylic glass with different lower rectangle widths and depths W_2 and Z , respectively, used for the experimental investigations. Three weir lower rectangle widths W_2 of 5, 7, and 9 cm and depths Z of 6, 9, and 11 cm were engaged. The semicircular gate below also had three diameters of 8, 12, and 15 cm. In addition, the case of employing the compound weir without the semicircular gate was considered. The mentioned dimensions were used interchangeably.

The accuracy of the discharge measurement is verified by measuring the water levels on the upstream side of the weir after completing the calibration procedure. Water levels were measured using a point gauge with a vernier scale, providing an accuracy of 1 mm. The point gauge was positioned at a location four times the maximum head over the weir upstream,

in accordance with [7]. Discharge is determined by measuring the head over the weir within the weir section, as the bottom boundary effect dictates that the flow through the weir section should be in free flow.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A total of 36 combined structure models were fabricated from acrylic glass sheets with different weir rectangles, W_2 and Z and semicircular gate diameter, d . Table I shows the form for each model, where W_2 and Z are the lower weir width and depth, respectively, and H is the height of the combined structure plate. Three weir lower rectangular widths W_2 of 5, 7, and 9 cm and depths Z of 6, 9, and 11 cm were used interchangeably with the diameter d of the semicircular gate having values of 8, 12, and 15 cm. Six experimental runs with different water heads for each setup were applied, which means that 216 experimental runs were carried out. The experimental programs are indicated in Table I.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL DIMENSIONS

Semicircular gate diameter, d (cm)	Lower weir width, W_2 (cm)	Lower weir depth, Z (cm)
0 (Weir only)	5	6, 9, and 11
	7	6, 9, and 11
	9	6, 9, and 11
8 cm	5	6, 9, and 11
	7	6, 9, and 11
	9	6, 9, and 11
12 cm	5	6, 9, and 11
	7	6, 9, and 11
	9	6, 9, and 11
15 cm	5	6, 9, and 11
	7	6, 9, and 11
	9	6, 9, and 11

The following procedure was consistently adopted for each experimental run. Firstly, the model was securely fixed at the end of the flume. Next, water was incrementally introduced into the flume until the desired head over the weir was achieved. To ensure the attainment of a steady state condition, the experiment was carried out with a consistent flow rate both over the weir and beneath the gate. Using the hydraulic bench, the actual discharge for each experimental run was determined by dividing the collected water volume by the corresponding time. The conclusion of each experimental run involved turning off the pump. This same procedure should be followed for the subsequent combined structure model.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main aim of this paper is to demonstrate the influence of a sharp compound weir comprising two rectangular components and a semicircular gate situated below as a hydraulic control device, on the combined structure discharge coefficient (C_d). Various dimensions, including the width (W_2) and depth (Z) of the lower weir rectangle, as well as the diameter (d) of the semicircular gate, were systematically varied in the conducted experimental runs. Upon analyzing the results obtained from these experiments, a comprehensive combined structure discharge coefficient equation was ultimately formulated through regression analysis.

A. Discharge Coefficient using the Compound Weir only (d=0)

The effect of the gate head ratio, h_2/H , on the compound weir discharge coefficient C_d for the flow passing through with different lower rectangle width and depth values in the absence of the semicircular gate is shown in Figures 3-5. The compound weir discharge coefficient C_d increases as the head ratio h_2/H increases for lower rectangle width W_2 of 5, 7, and 9 cm and depth Z of 6, 9, and 11 cm. For W_2 of 7 cm and Z of 9 cm, increasing the head h_2 from 10.5 cm to 16.5 cm (57.14%) results in increasing the compound weir discharge coefficient C_d from 0.612 to 0.875 (42.97%). Also, C_d increases as the W_2 increases, as shown in Figure 6. For example, for $h_2 = 16.1$ cm, increasing W_2 by 80% (from 5 to 9 cm) leads to 4.47% (0.819 to 0.856) increase in C_d . This happens because increasing h_2 or W_2 results in an increase in the theoretical discharge, Q_{th} , with a rate less than that of the actual discharge, Q_{act} , which in turn results in an increase in the C_d value. The compound weir discharge coefficient decreases as the Z increases (Figure 7). For $h_2 = 16.1$ cm and $W_2 = 7$ cm, increasing Z from 6 to 11 cm results in a decrease in C_d from 0.88 to 0.83, which means that 83.33% increasing in Z results in 6.02% decrease in C_d .

A general equation was developed to determine the discharge coefficient for the compound weir flow in the absence of the semicircular gate by analyzing the results and applying regression analysis.

$$C_d = 0.3517 \ln\left(\frac{h_2}{H}\right) + \left(5.638 \frac{W_2}{W} - 1.67\right) \frac{Z}{H} + 1.3164 \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3. Compound weir discharge coefficient C_d variation with h_2/H for $Z/H = 0.22$ and $d/H = 0$.

Fig. 4. Compound weir discharge coefficient C_d variation with h_2/H for $Z/H = 0.18$ and $d/H = 0$.

Fig. 5. Compound weir discharge coefficient C_d variation with h_2/H for $Z/H = 0.12$ and $d/H = 0$.

Fig. 6. Variation of C_d with W_2/W , for $h_2/H = 0.32$ and $d/H = 0$.

Fig. 7. Variation of C_d with z/H , for $h_2/H = 0.32$, and $d/H = 0$.

The compound discharge coefficient was computed using (8), which was determined to be a valid formula when applied to compound weir flow only, particularly when compared to the findings from earlier studies. Figure 8 illustrates the consistency between the calculated discharge coefficient, the measured discharge coefficient, and previous research results.

Fig. 8. Measured and calculated C_d for compound weir flow only ($d/H = 0$).

B. Discharge Coefficient using the Combined Structure ($d = 8, 12, \text{ and } 15 \text{ cm}$)

In this section, the discharge coefficient of the combined structure, which consists of the compound weir with the semicircular gate under it with diameters of 8, 12, and 15 cm, was calculated. For each semicircular diameter value, three values for the weir lower rectangle width of 5, 7, and 9 cm and depth of 6, 9, and 11 cm were used. Through the analysis of the obtained results, the discharge coefficient C_d for the compound weir with the semicircular gate under it increases as the water head h_2 increases (Figures 9–17).

Fig. 9. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.22 and d/H of 0.16.

For example, for a $W_2 = 7 \text{ cm}$, $d = 8 \text{ cm}$ and $Z = 9 \text{ cm}$, it was found that changing W_2 from 11.2 to 15.2 cm changes C_d from 0.663 to 0.73. Also, it was discovered that C_d has a direct proportional relationship with W_2 (Figures 18–20).

Fig. 10. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.18 and d/H of 0.16.

Fig. 11. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.12 and d/H of 0.16.

Fig. 12. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.22 and d/H of 0.24.

Fig. 13. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.18 and d/H of 0.24.

Fig. 14. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.12 and d/H of 0.24.

Fig. 15. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.22 and d/H of 0.30.

Fig. 16. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.18 and d/H of 0.30.

Fig. 17. Variation of C_d with h_2/H for Z/H of 0.12 and d/H of 0.30.

For instance, when W_2 changes from 5 to 9 cm for $d = 8$ cm, $Z = 9$ cm, and $h_2 = 15$ cm, it results in a change of C_d from 0.67 to 0.69. But the C_d of the combined structure has inversely proportional relationship with Z . It was found that for $d = 8$ cm, $h_2 = 15$ cm, and $W_2 = 7$ cm, increasing Z from 6 to 11 cm decreases C_d from 0.71 to 0.655, i.e., increasing Z by 83.33% leads to a decrease of 8.39% in C_d (Figures 21–23).

Fig. 18. Variation of C_d with W_2/W , for $h_2/H = 0.3$, $d/H = 0.16$.

Fig. 19. Variation of C_d with W_2/W , for $h_2/H = 0.3$, $d/H = 0.24$.

Fig. 20. Variation of C_d with W_2/W , for $h_2/H = 0.3$, $d/H = 0.3$.

Fig. 21. Variation of C_d with z/H , for $h_2/H = 0.3$, $d/H = 0.16$.

Fig. 22. Variation of C_d with z/H , for $h_2/H = 0.3$, $d/H = 0.24$.

Fig. 23. Variation of C_d with z/H , for $h_2/H = 0.3$, $d/H = 0.3$.

C. Developing General Mathematical Equations

The obtained experimental results were analyzed and utilized in the development of general empirical equations through the application of the dimensionless group regression method, which was taken into consideration when estimating the combined structure discharge coefficient. A correlation between the computed dimensionless groups and the dependent values of C_d was examined. The h_2/H , W_2/W , Z/H , and C_d dimensionless groups were found to have a significant correlation. The developed empirical equations are:

- For $d/H = 0.16$:

$$C_d = \left(-0.74 \left(\frac{W_2}{W} \right) + 0.259 \right) \ln \left(\frac{h_2}{H} \right) - 0.579 \frac{Z}{H} - 1.266 \frac{W_2}{W} + 1.1685 \quad (9)$$

- For $d/H = 0.24$:

$$C_d = \left(0.179 \left(\frac{W_2}{W} \right) + 0.111 \right) \ln \left(\frac{h_2}{H} \right) - 0.367 \frac{Z}{H} + 0.47 \frac{W_2}{W} + 0.803 \quad (10)$$

- For $d/H = 0.30$:

$$C_d = 0.054 \ln \left(\frac{h_2}{H} \right) + \left(5.878 \frac{W_2}{W} - 1.512 \right) \frac{Z}{H} - 0.77 \frac{W_2}{W} + 0.846 \quad (11)$$

These equations were validated using the experimentally measured results versus the calculated values for the discharge coefficient of the combined structure (Figures 24–26). The results show a good agreement between the experimental and the predicted values.

Fig. 24. Measured and calculated C_d for combined structure flow ($d/H = 0.16$).

Fig. 25. Measured and calculated C_d for combined structure flow ($d/H = 0.24$).

Fig. 26. Measured and calculated C_d for combined structure flow ($d/H = 0.30$).

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, experimental runs were conducted to explore the discharge coefficient of a combined hydraulic structure comprising a compound weir and a semicircular gate situated beneath it, under varying hydraulic and geometric conditions. The influence of parameters such as the water head over the weir lower rectangle sill (h_2), the water head over the below gate (h_3), the width of the weir lower rectangle (W_2), and its depth (Z), on the discharge coefficient were thoroughly investigated. The following conclusions were drawn:

- Based on the weir-gate width ratio, the combined structure conveyed greater discharge by approximately 2 to 10 times than the traditional rectangular notch weir, indicating that it is more effective than the traditional weir in terms of discharge capacity.
- The discharge coefficient values of the combined structure ranged from 0.46 to 0.89, with an average value of 0.675. The discharge coefficient increases when the head of water over the weir h_2/H increases for given W_2 , Z , and gate diameter d .
- For a given weir lower rectangle depth Z , water head h_2 , and gate diameter d , the discharge coefficient values of the combined structure increase by increasing the weir lower rectangle width ratio W_2/W .
- The developed general empirical equations can be used to calculate the discharge coefficient values of the combined structure for given h_2/H , W_2/W , and Z/H .

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Assessment of a Hybrid (Wind-Solar) System at High-Altitude Agriculture Regions for achieving Sustainable Development Goals

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ABSTRACT

Power generation from hybrid renewable energy systems is gaining popularity worldwide, especially in developing countries suffering from electricity crises. Small-scale hybrid wind and solar systems, especially in high-altitude agriculture regions, which may experience electricity shortages during extreme weather conditions, can be critical to achieving sustainability goals and objectives. The latter will be reached by providing clean energy and addressing economic concerns. Accordingly, the main aim of the current paper is to evaluate the techno-economic feasibility of a grid-connected hybrid (vertical axis wind turbine – 2-axis photovoltaic) system at high-altitude agriculture regions (Ardal and Faridan) in Iran for the production of clean energy. To this aim, the wind speed and solar radiation data were analyzed statistically using 13 distribution functions. The results indicate that Generalized Extreme Value produced the best fit for the wind speed and solar radiation data. Furthermore, the purpose of the current work is to evaluate the technical and economic aspects of grid-connected hybrid vertical axis wind turbines as well as PV tracking systems using RETScreen software. The results demonstrate that implementing the proposed system could generate significant amounts of electricity in order to meet the demand for domestic and agricultural applications while ensuring clean energy in line with sustainable development goals. Besides, this study can help integrate renewable energy into the grid and help policymakers facilitate the installation of rooftop small-scale hybrid systems in the future.

Keywords-wind; solar; techno-economic; hybrid system; vertical axis wind turbine; PV tracking systems

I. INTRODUCTION

The Sustainable Development Goals include seventeen global goals set by the United Nations General Assembly to promote a sustainable future for all [1]. These goals were officially adopted in 2015, with the aim to accomplish their widespread implementation by 2030 [2]. Concerning the Sustainable Development Goals, the advancement of renewable energy sources plays a pivotal role in achieving energy security in various sectors, including transportation, environmental

conservation, construction, economy, machinery, and industry [3]. Energy derived from renewable energy sources such as solar and wind energy, effectively meets the energy requirements while simultaneously promoting community development and global environmental conservation [4]. Renewable energy has emerged as a powerful solution to the energy crisis during the recent decades, offering a way to address the challenge while mitigating adverse impacts on climate and nature [5-7].

At present, Iran's heavy dependence on fossil fuels, especially natural gas and oil, has led to the need to diversify energy sources [8]. According to the World Bank, fossil fuel energy consumption accounts for approximately 99.02% of the total energy consumption, with the remaining 0.08% sourced from renewable energy. Therefore, energy remains a significant challenge in the country, despite the government's ongoing efforts to respond to the energy necessities of the population. The electric power consumption in Iran generally ranges from 2.31 to 5.67 kWh per capita (i.e. 2.927 kWh per capita) according to the World Bank. Consequently, there is a pressing need to fully harness the proven vast reserves of renewable energy resources to complement traditional energy sources, mitigate impending energy crises, and enhance electricity access for sustainable national development. Wind and solar energy are vital tools in the fight against climate change as the world confronts the escalating threat of global warming [9-11]. Their adoption is a strategic step toward a sustainable future [11]. Wind turbines and photovoltaic (PV) panels generate clean electricity, minimizing greenhouse gas emissions and reducing the carbon footprint [12]. Utilizing wind and solar energy can significantly reduce the reliance on fossil fuels, transforming the energy landscape [13]. This diversification enhances Iran's energy security, reducing the vulnerability to supply disruptions and price fluctuations in the global energy market.

The main goal of this paper is to evaluate the feasibility of harnessing wind energy and analyze the effectiveness of a grid-connected vertical axis wind turbine combined with a tracking photovoltaic system in high-altitude regions. In regions characterized by high altitudes, access to traditional energy grids can be limited, emphasizing the importance of renewable energy systems like wind and solar for meeting local energy demands [14]. Furthermore, the implementation of grid-connected renewable energy systems can enhance energy self-sufficiency and reduce reliance on long-distance energy transmission [15]. Accordingly, it is essential to assess the wind energy potential and the performance of grid-connected vertical axis wind turbines with tracking PV systems in high-altitude areas. These regions often feature stronger and more consistent wind resources, which can contribute to the expansion of renewable energy, decrease environmental impact, and bolster energy security in remote locations.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Study Area

Ardal (Latitude: 31.99°N, Longitude: 50.66°E, elevation: 1847 m) and Faridan (Latitude: 32.98°N, Longitude: 50.39°E, elevation: 2267 m) are two high-altitude areas located in Iran. Ardal and Faridan are regions located in the Chaharmahal and Bakhtiari Province in southwestern Iran and the Isfahan Province of central Iran, respectively. The economy of these selected locations is primarily based on agriculture, animal husbandry, and pastoral activities. In general, due to climate variability, agricultural demand, and changes in land use, both locations face the challenges of water scarcity. Moreover, both locations can experience extreme weather conditions, such as heavy snowfall, which can damage power lines and disrupt electricity supply.

B. Data Collection

The Modern-Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and Applications, Version 2 (MERRA-2), is a reanalysis dataset provided by NASA that offers a comprehensive record of the Earth's climate from 1980 onward [16]. MERRA-2 is an updated version of the original MERRA dataset, providing more accurate and detailed atmospheric data and climate information. It is commonly used by researchers and scientists for various climate, weather, and environmental studies [5, 13, 17-20]. MERRA-2 covers a wide range of atmospheric and environmental variables, including temperature, humidity, wind, precipitation, radiation, and more [21]. These variables are available at multiple altitudes and spatial resolutions. Additionally, it offers data on a global scale, making it suitable for research and analysis in various regions around the world. The mean monthly wind speed including minimum and maximum wind speed and solar radiation data were collected from 1981 to 2022 and 2001-2022, respectively.

C. Grid-on Wind-PV Hybrid System

A grid-connected Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT) and tracking photovoltaic (PV) system represent two distinct renewable energy technologies that can be integrated to generate electricity efficiently and sustainably. Combining a VAWT system with a tracking PV system allows for the simultaneous capture of wind and solar energy. This combination of renewable energy sources can contribute to a more reliable and sustainable energy supply, especially in areas with variable weather conditions [22]. In general, the grid-connected VAWT and PV components are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. COMPONENTS OF A WIND AND PV SYSTEM [13]

Grid-connected VAWT	Tracking PV system
VAWT: The central component of the system is the VAWT itself, which consists of vertical rotor blades connected to a vertical shaft. The rotor blades capture wind energy and transfer it to the generator.	Solar panels: Also known as PV modules, are made up of multiple solar cells that convert sunlight into electricity. In a tracking PV system, these panels are mounted on tracking structures.
Generator: The generator is responsible for converting the mechanical energy from the rotating VAWT blades into AC electrical energy.	Tracking Mechanism: The tracking mechanism includes motors and sensors that allow the solar panels to follow the sun's path across the sky. It can be a single-axis tracker, which follows the sun's east-west movement, or a dual-axis tracker, which follows both east-west and north-south movements.
Inverter: It is used to convert the AC generated by the VAWT into DC. This DC electricity can then be conditioned and synchronized with the grid's electrical characteristics.	Inverter: Converts the DC electricity generated by the solar panels into AC electricity compatible with the grid.
Grid Connection: A connection point to the electrical grid allows the system to feed the generated electricity into the grid for distribution and use.	Grid Connection: The PV system is connected to the electrical grid through a grid connection point, enabling the electricity generated by the solar panels to be fed into the grid.

The electricity generated by the VAWT and the PV systems is synchronized through inverters to ensure it is compatible

with the grid's electrical characteristics [23]. The combined output of wind and solar energy is then fed into the electrical grid for distribution and use. Calculating the capacity of an inverter for integrating a VAWT and a tracking PV system requires consideration of various factors, including the maximum power output of each system, their respective voltage levels, and any potential surges in power production. It can be done as follows:

- Determine the Maximum Power Outputs: Find out the maximum power output of the VAWT and the tracking PV system. These ratings represent the peak power that each system can produce under optimal conditions.
- Voltage Compatibility: (1) Determine the voltage output of the VAWT system. The VAWT often generates low-voltage DC power. (2) Determine the voltage output of your tracking PV system. Solar panels typically produce low-voltage DC power. Ensure that both systems' voltage levels are compatible with the chosen inverter. In most grid-connected systems, an inverter converts DC to AC power for grid synchronization.
- Add the peak power output of your VAWT system to the peak power output of your tracking PV system to get the total peak power.

It is common to oversize the inverter slightly to accommodate power surges or fluctuations. A 10-20% safety margin is often recommended. Selecting the right inverter capacity is crucial for the efficient and safe integration of your VAWT and tracking PV systems into the grid. Oversizing the inverter slightly and considering safety margins can help ensure that your renewable energy system performs optimally under varying conditions.

D. Probability Density Functions (PDFs)

PDFs provide a systematic way to analyze and understand the statistical properties of wind speed and solar radiation data [13]. They help summarize the data, making it easier to grasp central tendencies, variability, and extremes within the dataset. PDFs allow modeling the behavior of wind speed and solar radiation, which is crucial in various applications. PDFs are used to estimate the long-term energy potential of a location in renewable energy resource assessment [24]. This information is crucial for project development and investment decisions. In this study, 13 distribution functions (DFs) are utilized to represent the wind speed and solar radiation frequency distribution. These distributions are listed in Table II.

E. Wind Potential Estimation

Wind Power Density (WPD) is one of the most important indicators of wind potential for designing a wind farm. WPD is an indicator used to assess the potential of wind resources at a particular location. It can be determined by [25]:

$$\frac{P}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \bar{v}^3 \quad (1)$$

where P represents the wind power, ρ is the air density ($\rho = 1.23 \text{ kg/m}^3$), and \bar{v} is the mean wind speed in m/s.

Furthermore, the wind energy potential is categorized according to the average WPD at 10 m height [13, 25].

- Poor (WPD $\leq 100 \text{ W/m}^2$)
- Marginal (WPD $\leq 150 \text{ W/m}^2$)
- Moderate (WPD $\leq 200 \text{ W/m}^2$)
- Good (WPD $\leq 250 \text{ W/m}^2$)
- Excellent (WPD $\leq 300 \text{ W/m}^2$)

Wind speed data are typically collected at a consistent height of 10 m above the ground. To estimate wind speeds at different hub heights, the power law model is employed. This model is defined by [25]:

$$\frac{v}{v_{10}} = \left(\frac{z}{z_{10}} \right)^\alpha \quad (2)$$

where v is the wind speed at the wind turbine hub height z , v_{10} is the wind speed at the original height z_{10} , and α is the surface roughness coefficient, which depends on the characteristics of the region. The value of α can be determined by [25]:

$$\alpha = \frac{0.37 - 0.088 \ln(v_{10})}{1 - 0.088 \ln(z_{10}/2)} \quad (3)$$

F. Solar Potential Estimation

Solar energy potential was evaluated by categorizing it based on the annual Global Solar Radiation (GSR) amounts. GSR is considered a key parameter for assessing the energy generation potential of PV systems. The solar energy potential is classified based on the annual value of GSR as described below [10]:

- Poor (Annual GSR $< 1191.8 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)
- Marginal ($1191.8 < \text{Annual GSR} < 1419.7 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)
- Fair ($1419.7 < \text{Annual GSR} < 1641.8 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)
- Good ($1641.8 < \text{Annual GSR} < 1843.8 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)
- Excellent ($1843.8 < \text{Annual GSR} < 2035.9 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)
- Outstanding ($2035.9 < \text{Annual GSR} < 2221.8 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)
- Superb (Annual GSR $< 2221.8 \text{ kWh/m}^2$)

G. The Proposed Hybrid System

In this study, the viability of developing a 5 kW grid-connected hybrid system was examined from technical, financial, and environmental perspectives. Additionally, the monocrystalline silicon (mono-Si) PV module with the model JKM360M-76, featuring a power capacity of 360 W and an efficiency of 18.55%, was employed. The detailed specifications of the chosen PV module can be found in Table III. Furthermore, the SunSurfs WT3 Vertical Axis Wind Turbine with a rated capacity of 5 kW was chosen. The detailed specifications of the selected turbine are provided in Table IV.

TABLE II. DFS, PDFS, AND CUMULATIVE DFS

Distribution Function		Probability Density Function			Cumulative Distribution Function			
Normal (N)		$f(v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{v-\mu}{2\sigma^2}\right)$			$F(v) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma\sqrt{2}}\right)\right]$			
Gamma (G)		$f(v) = \frac{R^{\alpha-1}}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{\beta}\right)\right)$			$F(v) = \frac{\Gamma(R/\beta, \alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$			
Generalized Extreme Value (GEV)		$f(v) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sigma} \left[1 + \zeta \left(\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^{-1/\zeta}\right]^{\zeta+1} \exp\left(-\left(1 + \zeta \left(\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^{-1/\zeta}\right)^{-1/\zeta}\right) & k \neq 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sigma} \left[\exp\left(-\left(\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right)\right]^{\zeta+1} \exp\left(\exp\left(-\left(\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right)\right) & k = 0 \end{cases}$			$F(v) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\exp\left(-\left(\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right)\right) & k \neq 0 \\ \exp\left(-\exp\left(-\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right) & k = 0 \end{cases}$			
Nakagami (Na)		$f(v) = \frac{2m^m}{\Gamma(m)\Omega^m} v^{2m-1} e^{-\left(\frac{m}{\Omega}G^2\right)}$			$F(v) = \frac{\gamma\left(\frac{m}{\Omega}, \frac{v}{\Omega}\right)}{\Gamma(m)}$			
Inverse Gaussian (IG)		$f(v) = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{2\pi(R-\gamma)}} \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda(v-\mu)^2}{2\mu^2 R}\right)$			$F(v) = \Phi\left(\sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{R-\gamma}}\left(\frac{v}{\mu} - 1\right)\right) + \Phi\left(-\sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{R-\gamma}}\left(\frac{v}{\mu} + 1\right)\right) \exp\left(\frac{2\lambda}{\mu}\right)$			
Log-normal (LN)		$f(v) = \frac{1}{v\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\ln(v)-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2\right]$			$F(v) = \frac{1}{2} + \operatorname{erf}\left[\frac{\ln(v)-\mu}{\sigma\sqrt{2}}\right]$			
Log-Logistic (LL)		$f(v) = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{\beta}{\alpha}\left(\frac{v}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1}\right)}{\left(1 + \frac{v}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}\right)^2$			$F(v) = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{v}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}$			
Rayleigh (R)		$f(v) = \frac{v}{\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{v}{\sigma}\right)^2\right)$			$F(v) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{v}{\sigma}\right)^2\right)$			
Weibull (W)		$f(v) = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\sigma}\right)\left(\frac{v}{\sigma}\right)^{\alpha-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{\sigma}\right)^\alpha\right)$			$F(v) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v}{\sigma}\right)^\alpha\right)$			
Three-Parameter Weibull (W-3P)		$f(v) = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}\right)\left(\frac{v-\gamma}{\beta}\right)^{\alpha-1} \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v-\gamma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right)$			$F(v) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{v-\gamma}{\beta}\right)^\alpha\right)$			
Kumaraswamy (K)		$f(v) = \frac{abe}{\Gamma(\alpha)\beta^\alpha} \frac{1}{(1-v^\alpha)^2} \left(\frac{1-(1-v^\alpha)^b}{\beta(1-v^\alpha)^b}\right)^{\alpha-1}$			$F(v) = \int_0^v \frac{1-(1-v^\alpha)^b}{(1-v^\alpha)^b} \frac{e^{-\omega}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\beta^\alpha} d\omega = \frac{\Gamma(\alpha, z)}{\Gamma(\alpha)\beta^\alpha} \left(\alpha, \frac{1-(1-v^\alpha)^b}{\beta(1-v^\alpha)^b}\right)$			
Birnbaum-Saunders (BS)		$f(v) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{v-\mu}{\beta} + \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{v-\mu}}}}{2\gamma(v-\mu)} \phi\left(\frac{\sqrt{\frac{v-\mu}{\beta} + \sqrt{\frac{\beta}{v-\mu}}}}{\gamma}\right)$			$F(v) = \Phi\left(\frac{\sqrt{v-\mu}}{\gamma}\right)$			
Logistic (L)		$f(v) = \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)}{\sigma\{1+\exp\left(-\frac{v-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\}^2}$			$F(v) = \frac{1}{1+\exp(-v)}$			
N	σ	Standard deviation	Na	m	Shape parameter	LL	β	Shape parameter
	μ			Mean parameter	Ω		Scale parameter	α
G	β	Shape parameter	IG	λ	Shape parameter	W	α	Shape parameter
	α			Scale parameter	μ		Mean parameter	σ
GEV	μ	Location parameter	LN	σ	Shape parameter	W-3P	α	Shape parameter
	α			Scale parameter	μ		Scale parameter	σ
	ζ	Shape parameter	R	σ	Scale parameter		γ	Location parameter
K	a	Shape parameter	BS	μ	Location parameter	L	μ	Location parameter
	b			Scale parameter	β		Scale parameter	σ
	α	Shape parameter	γ	Shape parameter				
	β	Scale parameter						

TABLE III. SPECIFICATION OF THE SELECTED PV PANEL

Item	Specification	
Manufacturer	JinKO solar	
Model	JKM545M-72HL4-V	
	STC	NOCT
Maximum power (P_{max}) [W]	545	405
Voltage at maximum power (V_{mp}) [V]	40.8	38.25
Current at maximum power (I_{mpp}) [A]	13.36	10.60
Open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) [V]	49.52	46.74
Short circuit current (I_{sc}) [A]	13.94	11.26
Operating temperature range [°C]	-40°C~+85°C	
Temperature coefficient of P_{max} [%/°C]	-0.35%/°C	
Temperature coefficient of V_{oc} [%/°C]	-0.28%/°C	
Temperature coefficient of I_{sc} [%/°C]	0.048%/°C	
Nominal operating cell temperature (NOCT)	45±2°C	
Cost [USD/W]	0.37	

TABLE IV. WIND TURBINE CHARACTERISTICS

Variable	Value
Rated power [kW]	5
Startup wind speed [m/s]	1.8
Rated wind speed [m/s]	10
Survival wind speed [m/s]	28
Rated rotating speed [rpm]	40
Diameter [m]	18
Tower height [m]	14
Cost [USD]	15300

H. Simulation Software

Recently, various simulation tools have been utilized for evaluating the performance of wind farms, solar plants, and hybrid systems [20]. RETScreen is a widely used software tool for assessing energy production, life-cycle costs, emission reduction, financial viability, and risk for various types of renewable energy and energy efficiency projects [7]. It can be employed to rate the feasibility of grid-connected VAWTs and PV tracking systems, among other renewable energy projects. RETScreen is a versatile software tool that can appraise the technical and financial aspects of such hybrid renewable energy projects [7, 6].

Equations (4)-(11) represent the pre-defined mathematical expressions used by the tool [6, 7, 24] to perform the economic evaluation.

Capacity Factor (CF):

$$CF = \frac{P_{out}}{P \times 8760} \tag{4}$$

Annual GHG emission reduction (A-GHG):

$$A - GHG = [(Base\ case\ GHG\ emission\ factor) - (Proposed\ case\ GHG\ emission\ factor)] \times End\ use\ energy\ delivered \tag{5}$$

Net Present Value (NPV):

$$NPV = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{C_n}{(1+r)^n} \tag{6}$$

Levelized cost of energy (LCOE):

$$LCOE = \frac{sum\ of\ cost\ over\ lifetime}{s\ of\ electricity\ generated\ over\ lifetime} \tag{7}$$

Simple Payback (SP):

$$SP = \frac{C - IG}{(C_{ener} + C_{capa} + C_{RE} + C_{GHG}) - (C_{o\&M} + C_{fuel})} \tag{8}$$

Equity Payback (EP):

$$EP = \sum_{n=0}^N C_n \tag{9}$$

Annual Life Cycle Savings (ALCS):

$$ALCS = \frac{NPV}{\frac{1}{r} \left(1 - \frac{1}{(1+r)^N} \right)} \tag{10}$$

Benefit-Cost (B-C) ratio:

$$B - C = \frac{NPV + (1 - f_d)C}{(1 - f_d)C} \tag{11}$$

where P_{out} is the energy generated per year, P is the installed capacity, N is the project life in years, C_n is the after-tax cash flow in year n , r is the discount rate, C is the total initial cost of the project, f_d is the debt ratio, B is the total benefit of the project, IG represents the incentives and grants, C_{ener} is the annual energy savings or income. C_{capa} is the annual capacity savings or income, C_{RE} is the annual Renewable Energy (RE) production credit income, C_{GHG} is the GHG reduction income, $C_{o\&M}$ is the yearly operation and maintenance costs incurred by the clean energy project, C_{fuel} is the annual cost of fuel, which is zero for renewable projects, and Δ_{GHG} is the annual GHG emission reduction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Assessment of Wind Energy Potential

Figure 1 shows the mean monthly variation of wind speed for the selected locations. The statistical description of average monthly wind speed includes mean, Standard Deviation (SD), Coefficient of Variation (CV), minimum (Min.), maximum (Max.), Kurtosis (K), and Skewness (S), which are summarized in Table V. It is found that the mean wind speeds are within the range of 2.51-3.07 m/s for Ardal and 3.14-3.89 m/s for Faridan. Generally, the mean and SD values indicate a high level of consistency in wind behavior. Furthermore, it is evident that the CV values exhibit moderate levels, spanning from 10.21% to 24.5% for Ardal and 10.58% to 28.35% for Faridan. Additionally, we observe that the lowest monthly wind speeds, 1.81 m/s and 2.12 m/s, were recorded in November 2010 and November 1996, respectively. On the other hand, Faridan records the highest monthly wind speed at 6.48 m/s. Moreover, most locations display positive S values, signaling right-skewed data distributions. The K values, ranging from -1.56 to 7.79, signify variations in the flatness of the data distributions. A negative kurtosis (-1.56) suggests a slightly flatter distribution, while a positive kurtosis (7.79) implies heavier-tailed data compared to a normal distribution. As mentioned above, 13 distribution functions were utilized for analyzing the characteristics of wind speed at the selected location. Based on the findings, the GEV distribution function offers superior fits (best Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) values) for the wind speed data as shown in Table VI. Figure 2 involves the graphical representation of the PDF for all selected DFs. To assess the wind potential at the chosen location, the WPD was calculated. Its values were 13.97 W/m² and 26.48 W/m² for Ardal and

Faridan, respectively. Based on the WPD values obtained, the selected locations fall into power class 1, signifying relatively poor wind energy potential. Therefore, it is most suitable to utilize small-scale wind turbines in these regions to harness the available wind energy resources effectively.

Fig. 1. Monthly variation of mean wind speed for (a) Ardal, (b) Faridan.

B. Assessment of Solar Energy Potential

Figure 3 illustrates the mean monthly variation of Solar Radiation (SR) for the chosen locations. The statistical description of monthly average SR is summarized in Table VII. The mean monthly SR falls within the range of 5.54-6.29 kWh/m²/day for Ardal and 5.16-6.14 kWh/m²/day for Faridan, suggesting a notably consistent pattern based on the mean and standard deviation values. Furthermore, the S values for most locations are positive, denoting that all the distributions are right-skewed. It is found that the annual value of GHI is 2280.89 kWh/m² for Ardal and 2235.06 kWh/m² for Faridan. The analysis reveals that the solar resources in the chosen locations are categorized into the superb potential. In addition, the chosen DFs parameters were determined using the maximum likelihood method with monthly SR data. To ascertain the most appropriate distribution among the ten options for each location, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test was employed. Table VIII provides a summary of the estimated distribution parameters for all selected models, including the KS values and their corresponding ranks. According to the results, the GEV distribution function demonstrated the lowest KS value, implying that it offers the best fit for the SR data.

Fig. 2. Comparisons of PDF distributions for analyzing wind speed data (a) Ardal, (b) Faridan.

Fig. 3. Monthly variation of mean SR for (a) Ardal, (b) Faridan.

Figure 4 illustrates the graphical representation of the PDFs for all selected DFs.

C. Techno-Economic Analysis

Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA) for a grid-connected hybrid renewable energy system is crucial for financial decision-making. TEA helps assess the economic feasibility of the project by estimating costs, revenues, and potential returns on investment. This information is vital for investors, project developers, and financial institutions to make informed decisions. Also, it helps quantify reductions in greenhouse gas emissions and other pollutants, contributing to sustainability goals. In this study, TEA for the developed system was

conducted using the RETScreen software. To make the system feasible, this study utilizes various financial parameters as input variables, such as 7% inflation rate, 12% discount rate, 9% reinvestment rate, 70% debt ratio, 0% debt interest rate, and 5% electricity export escalation rate. These values were assumed based on previous scientific studies.

Figure 5 depicts the monthly Electricity Generation Exported (EGE) to the grid by a 5 kW grid-connected hybrid system. The data shows that the highest EGE values occur in June for the PV system and in March for the wind system. Conversely, the lowest EGE values are observed in December for the PV system and in September for the wind system.

TABLE V. STATISTICAL DESCRIPTION OF AVERAGE MONTHLY WIND SPEED FOR ALL SELECTED LOCATIONS

Year	Ardal							Faridan						
	Mean	SD	CV	Min.	Max.	S	K	Mean	SD	CV	Min.	Max.	S	K
1981	3.07	0.49	16.09	2.28	4.04	0.30	0.26	3.89	0.80	20.51	2.63	5.34	0.18	-0.36
1982	2.80	0.31	10.98	2.37	3.46	0.68	0.70	3.39	0.44	12.97	2.76	4.20	0.21	-0.61
1983	2.87	0.41	14.22	2.25	3.66	0.11	-0.26	3.54	0.58	16.40	2.81	4.88	1.06	1.31
1984	2.95	0.45	15.29	2.27	3.66	0.36	-0.93	3.71	0.70	18.75	2.69	4.96	0.47	-0.29
1985	2.87	0.54	18.85	2.06	4.25	1.28	3.72	3.77	0.98	25.84	2.61	6.48	2.01	5.80
1986	2.89	0.36	12.42	2.28	3.51	0.21	-0.33	3.45	0.46	13.24	2.70	4.27	0.35	-0.21
1987	2.96	0.44	14.90	2.57	3.92	1.34	0.86	3.77	0.71	18.78	2.94	5.14	0.58	-0.50
1988	3.06	0.48	15.83	2.31	4.18	0.82	2.06	3.79	0.79	20.72	2.68	5.66	0.94	2.34
1989	2.75	0.38	13.68	2.24	3.40	0.24	-0.85	3.32	0.45	13.60	2.68	3.94	-0.17	-1.06
1990	2.90	0.40	13.96	2.14	3.46	-0.29	-0.56	3.59	0.49	13.59	2.65	4.43	-0.30	0.17
1991	2.90	0.47	16.18	2.16	3.70	-0.06	-0.35	3.59	0.61	16.92	2.57	4.81	0.54	0.49
1992	3.00	0.48	16.03	2.04	3.88	-0.22	0.54	3.71	0.64	17.15	2.55	4.99	0.32	0.75
1993	2.79	0.46	16.30	2.12	3.60	0.13	-0.63	3.53	0.50	14.15	2.84	4.34	0.13	-1.17
1994	2.88	0.38	13.23	2.20	3.63	0.22	0.44	3.64	0.50	13.59	2.75	4.78	0.70	2.24
1995	2.51	0.27	10.56	1.89	2.79	-1.18	1.59	3.14	0.33	10.58	2.52	3.65	-0.39	-0.49
1996	2.75	0.49	17.88	1.91	3.53	-0.11	-0.86	3.33	0.63	18.80	2.12	4.15	-0.25	-0.52
1997	2.75	0.44	15.86	2.03	3.66	0.52	0.65	3.49	0.63	17.97	2.41	4.57	0.32	-0.51
1998	2.84	0.51	17.91	1.91	3.71	0.08	-0.11	3.52	0.62	17.62	2.70	4.66	0.74	-0.30
1999	2.80	0.37	13.30	2.24	3.28	-0.23	-1.56	3.47	0.57	16.45	2.61	4.32	0.10	-1.22
2000	2.81	0.45	15.90	2.11	3.55	0.15	-1.11	3.46	0.58	16.82	2.66	4.53	0.31	-0.83
2001	2.76	0.36	13.17	2.12	3.33	-0.04	-0.71	3.50	0.41	11.71	2.95	4.18	0.17	-1.13
2002	2.83	0.43	15.31	2.04	3.47	-0.43	-0.63	3.57	0.76	21.30	2.47	4.90	-0.03	-0.84
2003	2.87	0.48	16.84	2.41	3.79	1.23	0.31	3.57	0.65	18.15	2.95	4.84	1.30	0.61
2004	2.83	0.35	12.51	2.23	3.38	-0.05	-0.60	3.52	0.59	16.68	2.68	4.83	0.78	1.14
2005	2.71	0.30	10.90	2.37	3.38	1.13	1.06	3.30	0.46	13.97	2.72	4.52	1.72	4.23
2006	2.74	0.34	12.45	2.19	3.38	0.06	-0.11	3.40	0.49	14.43	2.87	4.31	0.85	-0.39
2007	2.74	0.39	14.29	2.08	3.51	0.49	0.65	3.44	0.58	16.79	2.29	4.41	-0.33	0.34
2008	2.80	0.32	11.53	2.24	3.33	-0.30	-0.39	3.36	0.51	15.32	2.68	4.33	0.57	-0.30
2009	2.73	0.39	14.31	2.12	3.27	0.08	-1.11	3.48	0.66	18.87	2.70	4.47	0.62	-1.04
2010	2.64	0.45	17.17	1.81	3.25	-0.52	-0.75	3.32	0.72	21.73	2.15	4.39	0.10	-1.17
2011	2.91	0.33	11.38	2.30	3.51	-0.10	0.35	3.45	0.47	13.52	2.79	4.43	0.88	0.72
2012	2.87	0.70	24.56	2.12	4.57	1.34	2.07	3.47	0.98	28.35	2.55	6.03	1.74	3.63
2013	2.83	0.36	12.78	2.01	3.32	-0.77	1.31	3.51	0.55	15.64	2.77	4.61	0.62	-0.22
2014	2.70	0.28	10.21	2.20	3.10	-0.62	-0.51	3.33	0.41	12.36	2.69	4.20	0.67	0.42
2015	2.94	0.40	13.66	2.48	3.66	0.58	-1.14	3.63	0.60	16.42	2.80	4.69	0.59	-0.74
2016	2.94	0.39	13.40	2.52	3.84	1.39	1.67	3.68	0.61	16.50	3.01	5.11	1.33	1.78
2017	2.93	0.38	12.81	2.30	3.29	-0.94	-0.80	3.58	0.41	11.41	2.70	4.13	-0.70	0.45
2018	2.75	0.33	11.94	2.24	3.18	-0.14	-1.41	3.38	0.54	16.00	2.77	4.45	0.51	-0.55
2019	2.85	0.50	17.56	2.02	3.56	0.14	-0.89	3.42	0.76	22.36	2.39	4.94	0.69	-0.24
2020	2.83	0.50	17.50	2.19	3.90	0.67	0.64	3.36	0.75	22.41	2.44	5.23	1.31	2.70
2021	2.71	0.40	14.58	2.30	3.84	2.36	6.71	3.38	0.57	16.89	2.69	5.05	2.46	7.79
2022	2.90	0.63	21.61	1.92	4.27	0.64	1.08	3.49	0.94	26.95	2.28	5.67	1.02	1.48

TABLE VI. DF PARAMETERS AND P-VALUE BASED ON THE KS TEST FOR ANALYZING WIND SPEED DATA

DF	Ardal				DF	Faridan			
	Parameters		Statistic	Rank		Parameters		Statistic	Rank
GEV	$k=-0.16507 \quad \sigma=0.27731 \quad \mu=2.7116$		0.11588	1	GEV	$k=-0.07426 \quad \sigma=0.37932 \quad \mu=3.3123$		0.10576	1
Na	$m=24.819 \quad \Omega=8.095$		0.13259	2	W-3P	$\alpha=1.6117 \quad \beta=0.72886 \quad \gamma=2.8493$		0.11904	2
W	$\alpha=11.199 \quad \beta=2.9025$		0.13349	3	G	$\alpha=70.049 \quad \beta=0.05004$		0.12537	3
G	$\alpha=99.74 \quad \beta=0.0284$		0.13431	4	Na	$m=17.104 \quad \Omega=12.447$		0.1269	4
N	$\sigma=0.28359 \quad \mu=2.8322$		0.13655	5	LN	$\sigma=0.11298 \quad \mu=1.2478$		0.12784	5
LL	$\alpha=15.845 \quad \beta=2.7759$		0.14002	6	BS	$\alpha=0.1131 \quad \beta=3.4828$		0.1279	6
W-3P	$\alpha=1.4275 \quad \beta=0.45671 \quad \gamma=2.4141$		0.14521	7	LL	$\alpha=13.698 \quad \beta=3.4177$		0.13203	7
BS	$\alpha=0.09561 \quad \beta=2.8193$		0.14568	8	N	$\sigma=0.41879 \quad \mu=3.5051$		0.13851	8
LN	$\sigma=0.09554 \quad \mu=1.0365$		0.14575	9	W	$\alpha=9.6125 \quad \beta=3.6$		0.14096	9
IV	$\lambda=282.48 \quad \mu=2.8322$		0.14717	10	IG	$\lambda=245.53 \quad \mu=3.5051$		0.14141	10
L	$\sigma=0.15635 \quad \mu=2.8322$		0.15788	11	L	$\sigma=0.23089 \quad \mu=3.5051$		0.15542	11
K	$\alpha_1=0.61943 \quad \alpha_2=1.1245 \quad a=2.4402 \quad b=3.3493$		0.20313	12	K	$\alpha_1=0.91493 \quad \alpha_2=0.70462 \quad a=2.7775 \quad b=4.2843$		0.26401	12
R	$\sigma=2.2598$		0.44181	13	R	$\sigma=2.7967$		0.4186	13

TABLE VII. STATISTICAL DESCRIPTION OF AVERAGE MONTHLY SOLAR RADIATION FOR ALL SELECTED LOCATIONS

Year	Ardal							Faridan						
	Mean	SD	CV	Min.	Max.	S	K	Mean	SD	CV	Min.	Max.	S	K
2001	6.28	1.66	26.48	2.99	8.47	-0.67	-0.18	5.71	2.10	36.75	2.46	8.38	-0.53	-1.09
2002	6.15	1.95	31.65	3.45	8.92	0.01	-1.61	5.69	2.09	36.68	2.92	8.62	0.08	-1.72
2003	5.98	1.86	31.04	3.55	8.49	0.01	-1.70	5.70	1.96	34.40	3.01	8.36	0.03	-1.56
2004	6.05	1.98	32.73	3.06	8.63	-0.09	-1.79	5.55	1.99	35.88	2.96	8.05	-0.06	-1.96
2005	6.16	2.01	32.62	3.20	9.49	0.03	-1.23	5.70	2.19	38.36	2.55	9.12	-0.09	-1.16
2006	5.86	2.01	34.25	3.03	9.06	0.04	-1.23	5.30	2.43	45.89	2.17	9.14	0.11	-1.35
2007	5.72	1.92	33.46	3.46	8.20	-0.02	-1.92	5.20	2.06	39.69	2.59	8.11	0.07	-1.58
2008	5.86	1.43	24.40	2.71	8.25	-0.67	1.21	5.47	1.59	29.03	2.68	8.08	-0.27	-0.63
2009	5.54	1.64	29.64	2.99	7.92	0.07	-1.09	5.16	1.66	32.16	2.65	7.36	-0.02	-1.33
2010	5.88	1.49	25.38	3.07	7.96	-0.45	-0.72	5.56	1.56	28.00	2.95	7.62	-0.36	-0.99
2011	5.71	1.64	28.80	3.06	8.17	-0.20	-1.14	5.35	1.74	32.56	2.57	7.86	-0.33	-1.11
2012	5.64	1.49	26.36	3.36	7.67	0.17	-1.44	5.37	1.53	28.50	3.52	7.36	0.26	-1.70
2013	6.14	1.54	25.12	4.07	8.60	0.19	-1.52	5.74	1.73	30.19	3.76	8.33	0.30	-1.55
2014	5.85	1.63	27.75	3.08	8.47	-0.01	-0.72	5.26	1.72	32.75	2.39	7.69	-0.11	-0.97
2015	5.70	1.51	26.44	3.31	8.15	-0.06	-0.65	5.39	1.60	29.66	3.10	8.03	0.03	-0.85
2016	6.29	1.54	24.41	3.66	8.64	-0.25	-1.04	5.78	1.71	29.60	3.37	8.22	-0.21	-1.44
2017	6.10	1.68	27.47	4.09	9.84	0.84	0.63	6.14	1.75	28.56	4.06	9.93	0.80	0.32
2018	5.61	1.75	31.20	3.24	8.56	0.26	-1.01	5.36	1.90	35.37	3.08	8.44	0.52	-1.27
2019	5.91	1.75	29.57	3.02	9.03	0.20	-0.54	5.65	1.66	29.31	2.81	8.22	0.07	-0.82
2020	6.16	1.83	29.71	4.30	9.74	0.59	-0.85	5.85	1.65	28.18	4.28	9.15	0.75	-0.58
2021	6.24	1.50	23.95	3.78	9.05	0.14	-0.26	6.00	1.45	24.21	4.07	9.06	0.72	0.21
2022	5.90	1.64	27.78	3.96	8.40	0.22	-1.72	5.92	1.59	26.88	3.50	8.22	0.08	-1.56

TABLE VIII. DF PARAMETER AND P-VALUE BASED ON KS TEST FOR ANALYZING SR DATA

DF	Ardal				DF	Faridan			
	Parameters		Statistic	Rank		Parameters		Statistic	Rank
GEV	$k=-0.18925 \quad \sigma=1.5589 \quad \mu=5.2919$		0.16969	1	GEV	$k=-0.21368 \quad \sigma=1.6772 \quad \mu=4.914$		0.14995	1
G	$\alpha=14.136 \quad \beta=0.42034$		0.17318	2	G	$\alpha=11.259 \quad \beta=0.49594$		0.16301	2
W	$\alpha=3.8606 \quad \beta=6.3056$		0.17328	3	Na	$m=3.1487 \quad \Omega=33.718$		0.16604	3
IG	$\lambda=83.995 \quad \mu=5.9419$		0.17961	4	BS	$\alpha=0.2979 \quad \beta=5.3465$		0.16733	4
BS	$\alpha=0.26135 \quad \beta=5.7456$		0.17983	5	LN	$\sigma=0.29609 \quad \mu=1.6772$		0.16735	5
LN	$\sigma=0.26018 \quad \mu=1.7487$		0.18013	6	LL	$\alpha=4.7379 \quad \beta=5.1435$		0.16888	6
Na	$m=3.8188 \quad \Omega=37.596$		0.18483	7	IG	$\lambda=62.87 \quad \mu=5.5839$		0.16918	7
W-3P	$\alpha=0.82014 \quad \beta=2.2016 \quad \gamma=3.8836$		0.18527	8	W	$\alpha=3.3814 \quad \beta=5.9625$		0.17315	8
N	$\sigma=1.5804 \quad \mu=5.9419$		0.19608	9	N	$\sigma=1.6641 \quad \mu=5.5839$		0.17425	9
LL	$\alpha=5.4193 \quad \beta=5.5401$		0.20239	10	L	$\sigma=0.91748 \quad \mu=5.5839$		0.19407	10
K	$\alpha_1=0.97025 \quad \alpha_2=1.0674 \quad a=3.8836 \quad b=8.6518$		0.21235	11	W-3P	$\alpha=0.86229 \quad \beta=1.9416 \quad \gamma=3.3727$		0.23268	11
L	$\sigma=0.87131 \quad \mu=5.9419$		0.21723	12	K	$\alpha_1=0.75667 \quad \alpha_2=1.5287 \quad a=3.3727 \quad b=8.6812$		0.23604	12
R	$\sigma=4.7409$		0.28503	13	R	$\sigma=4.4553$		0.24914	13

Based on the findings in Table IX, the following can be concluded:

- In Faridan, the PV system produces the most electricity annually, reaching a peak of 10,932.52 kWh. The minimum

annual electricity generation from the PV system is 10,283.56 kWh in Ardal. On average, the PV system generates around 10,608.04 kWh per year.

Fig. 4. PDF distributions comparison for analyzing SR data: (a) Ardal and (b) Faridan.

- Faridan also records the highest annual electricity generation from the wind system, with a maximum of 8,933.17 kWh. In Ardal, the wind system's annual generation is at its lowest, with a minimum of 6,724.77 kWh. On average, the wind system generates approximately 7,828.97 kWh annually.
- The efficiency of the PV system in Faridan reaches a maximum capacity factor of 24.96%, indicating effective utilization of the available sunlight. In Ardal, the PV system's capacity factor is at its lowest, with a minimum of 23.81%. On average, the PV system operates at a capacity factor of approximately 24.38%.
- Similarly, in Faridan, the wind system achieves a maximum capacity factor of 20.40%, showcasing its efficient conversion of available wind energy into electricity. In Ardal, the wind system's capacity factor is the lowest at 15.35%. On average, the wind system maintains a capacity factor of approximately 17.88%.
- The maximum simple payback period is 15.17 years in Ardal, the minimum is 12.99 years in Faridan, and the average is approximately 14.08 years. Similarly, the maximum equity payback period is 6.68 years in Ardal, the minimum is 5.41 years in Faridan, and the average is approximately 6.05 years.
- The maximum NPV is \$9,377.86 in Faridan, the minimum is \$5,945.58 in Ardal, and the average is approximately USD 7,161.72. A positive NPV not only demonstrates financial viability but also underscores the long-term sustainability of renewable energy projects by reducing energy costs and potentially generating revenue from

excess energy production. Furthermore, the environmental benefits of reduced greenhouse gas emissions are implicit. Additionally, ALCS quantifies the annual financial savings generated by the project. In this context, the highest annual savings are USD 1,195.68/year in Faridan, while the lowest is USD 758.06/year in Ardal. The average ALCS is approximately USD 976.87/year.

- Energy Production Cost (EPC) signifies the cost of producing 1 kWh of electricity. It is found that the maximum cost is 0.1086 kWh/USD in Ardal and the minimum is 0.0930 kWh/USD in Faridan, whereas the average is approximately 0.1008 kWh/USD.
- Reducing GHG emissions promotes environmental sustainability by lowering the carbon footprint. It is found that the reduction is 11.48 tCO₂ in Faridan and 9.82 tCO₂ in Ardal, while the average is approximately 10.65 tCO₂

Fig. 5. Monthly variation of EGE of proposed systems.

TABLE IX. DF PARAMETERS AND P-VALUE BASED ON THE KS TEST FOR ANALYZING SR DATA

Parameters	Ardal	Faridan
Annual-PV system [kWh]	10283.56	10932.52
Annual wind system [kWh]	6724.77	8933.17
Capacity factor -PV system [%]	23.81	24.96
Capacity factor -wind system [%]	15.35	20.40
Gross annual GHG emission reduction [tCO ₂]	9.82	11.48
Simple payback [Year]	15.17	12.99
Equity payback [Year]	6.68	5.41
Net Present Value [USD]	5945.58	9377.86
Annual life cycle savings [USD/year]	758.06	1195.68
Energy production cost [kWh/USD]	0.1086	0.0930

Moreover, yearly cash flows in terms of cumulative and pre-tax values are crucial for assessing the financial viability

and attractiveness of a project. They provide a comprehensive view of a project's financial performance over time, including its ability to generate returns on investment and its economic sustainability. These metrics aid decision-makers, investors, and project developers in evaluating projects and making informed financial and strategic choices. Cumulative cash flows represent the running total of cash inflows and outflows over time, usually on an annual basis. They accumulate year by year and provide insight into the project's overall financial performance throughout its lifespan. Cumulative cash flows help stakeholders understand the project's financial trajectory, including when it starts generating profits or returns on investment. They are crucial because they reveal the project's

financial health over time and whether it is on track to recover its initial investment and generate a profit. Pre-tax cash flows refer to the cash inflows and outflows before accounting for income taxes. They are important because they reflect the project's financial performance in its purest form, without the influence of tax considerations. Analyzing pre-tax cash flows allows stakeholders to assess the project's economic viability and profitability based solely on its operational and financial characteristics. It helps in making investment decisions and evaluating the project's attractiveness to potential investors. Figure 6 provides an overview of the cash flow throughout the lifespan of wind farm and solar plant projects in the chosen region.

Fig. 6. Cumulative and pre-tax cash flow for all projects.

IV. DISCUSSION

The Sustainable Development Goals provide an inspiring framework for energy sector initiatives and policies, guiding them towards sustainability. Global energy demand is rising, leading to increased carbon emissions and environmental degradation. In response, Sustainable Development Goal 7 aims to provide "modern, reliable, and environmentally friendly energy for all" by 2030 [26]. Solar and wind energy undoubtedly support these endeavors and enhance technical and economic efforts to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals. An example of these ambitious projects is the installation of grid-connected vertical-axis hybrid wind turbines and PV tracking systems in high-altitude areas, representing a major step towards sustainable goals. High-altitude solar and wind energy are widely considered the most promising sources of renewable energy [27]. This paper represented the examination of high-altitude wind and solar energy potential in

the regions of Ardal and Faridan, Iran for the first time utilizing the MERRA-2 dataset. To analyze the characteristics of wind and solar radiation data, 13 distribution functions were employed. According to the study's results, it was observed that the GEV DF displayed the lowest KS value. This shows that the GEV DF provides the best fit for the wind speed and solar radiation data, suggesting its suitability for modeling these datasets. Moreover, the obtained WPD values categorize the selected locations into power class 1, which signifies relatively low wind energy potential. Consequently, it is advisable to employ small-scale wind turbines in these areas to efficiently tap into the limited wind energy resources. On the other hand, both locations exhibit superb solar potential, suggesting that they are highly suitable for harnessing solar energy resources. Furthermore, this paper presented a technical and economic feasibility study of a VAWT and PV tracking system for electricity production.

Based on the findings of this study, it has been determined that the total energy production from the hybrid system is 17,008.33 kWh for Ardal and 19,865.69 kWh for Faridan. Moreover, the PV system competence varies between the two regions, with Faridan achieving a maximum capacity factor of 24.96%, denoting effective utilization of available sunlight, while Ardal achieved 23.81%, with an average of approximately 24.38%. Similarly, in Faridan, the wind system demonstrates efficiency with a maximum capacity factor of 20.40%, successfully converting wind resources into electricity. In contrast, Ardal's wind system has the lowest capacity factor at 15.35%, with an approximate average of 17.88%. These results are supported by several previous studies. As mentioned in [28], the economic viability of a project is measured by considering its NPV and payback period. In the case of this project, the NPV, which represents the disparity between the present value of cash inflows and cash outflows over a specific time frame for all locations, yielded positive results. This positive NPV signifies that the project is financially and economically viable [29-32]. Besides, it is observed that simple and equity payback period is within the range of 12.99-15.17 years and 5.41-6.68 years, respectively. These results are in accordance with the findings of several previous studies. For example, authors in [31] reported CF values ranging from 31.1% to 49% for 50 m hub-height turbines and 37.3% to 56.6% for 75m hub-height turbines. Authors in [33] observed varying values for simple payback and CF in the range of 1.9 to 27.3 years and 4.5% to 37.2%, respectively, for a BWT 61 m–800 kW wind turbine. In [34], it was found that the payback period for various 100 MW wind farms ranged from 6.34 to 19.9 years. Authors in [35] noted that CF values for various wind turbines fell between 32% and 38%. Authors in [36] reported CF values spanning from 6.8% to 47.6% for different wind turbines with varying characteristics. Authors in [32] proposed a PV system had an annual CF ranging from 20.70% to 21.70%. Authors in [32] found that the payback period for their developed PV system ranged from 13.6 to 14.6 years. Authors in [37] reported annual CF values ranging from 17.5% to 20.03% and simple payback period values within the range of 6.38 years to 7.00 years. Authors in [38] outlined a CF value of 22 for 12.25 kW grid-connected PV systems.

Moreover, this study's findings reveal that the highest energy production cost is 0.1086 kWh/USD in Ardal, while the lowest is 0.0930 kWh/USD in Faridan, with an average of approximately 0.1008 kWh/USD. These outcomes are corroborated by several scientific investigations. For example, authors in [33] observed that the LCOE for a 61 m–800 kW BWT wind turbine falls in the range of 0.04-0.43 USD. Authors in [35] noted LCOE values ranged from 0.255 USD/kWh to 0.306 USD/kWh. Authors in [36] reported CF values spanning from 6.8% to 47.6% for different wind turbines with diverse characteristics. Authors in [5] described LCOE values varying from 0.08703 USD/kWh to 0.01025 USD/kWh for a 5 kW Vertical Axis Wind Generator-V and LCOE values ranging from 0.036 USD/kWh to 0.049 USD/kWh for a 5 kW grid-connected PV system. Authors in [32] reported LCOE values for their proposed PV system varying from 0.128 USD/kWh to 0.135 USD/kWh. Authors in

[38] estimated an LCOE value of 0.0382 USD/kWh for a developed PV system.

According to the Iran Energy Report 2022, electricity cost has shown an annual rise of approximately 20% since 2019, reaching 0.0024 USD/kWh for households and 0.0034 USD/kWh for industrial consumers in 2021. It is found that the energy production cost from the proposed system is higher than the electricity tariff. However, there are still several benefits from the developed systems such as (1) reduced reliance on external power sources, especially in remote areas or during power outages, (2) reduced greenhouse gas emissions and carbon footprint, (3) provision of a stable electricity source and reduced vulnerability to energy price fluctuations, (4) earning income through net metering or feed-in tariffs, and (5) leading to more stable and efficient energy infrastructure.

Additionally, the gross annual greenhouse gas emission reduction quantifies the decrease in greenhouse gas emissions attributable to the renewable energy project. These emissions are significant contributors to global warming and climate change. The study reported 11.48 tCO₂ reduction in Faridan, and 9.82 tCO₂ in Ardal, with an average of around 10.65 tCO₂. By mitigating these tons of CO₂ equivalent, the project contributes to the realization of Sustainable Development Goal 15 (SDG 15): Life on Land.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTUER WORK

The case study in this research demonstrates the possible technical and economic feasibility and develops a system to meet household energy needs. This research can serve as a framework to evaluate the practicability of the prospective small-scale hybrid wind system in Iran and other developing countries. In future studies, a hardware implementation of the system suggested may be carried out with detailed performance analysis, paving the way for its eventual dissemination and widespread adoption.

Exploring the achievability of wind and solar power in high-altitude areas is essential to maximizing renewable energy sources. These regions offer unique advantages, including stronger, more consistent wind patterns and greater exposure to sunlight. Harnessing these resources not only enhances clean energy production but also carries environmental benefits. It reduces greenhouse gas emissions, combats climate change, and has the potential to improve air quality. Furthermore, this transformation creates opportunities for sustainable development and job creation, thus benefiting local communities socially and economically. Such systems also hold the promise of improved public health, thanks to reduced pollution and cleaner air. Hence, prioritizing the environmental impact assessment of small-scale hybrid systems (wind and solar) to enhance the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies should be the main focus of future research. Besides, a comprehensive risk analysis of small-scale hybrid systems, incorporating wind and solar energy sources, is essential to assess the financial viability of such projects in the future. This analysis should entail various factors, including political, regulatory, and market risks, which can significantly impact these initiatives success. A thorough risk analysis should consider these factors, employ risk mitigation strategies,

and develop contingency plans to ensure the financial viability of small-scale hybrid systems. This will help project developers, investors, and policymakers make informed decisions and increase the likelihood of renewable energy projects to be successful.

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Investigation of the Experimental Shear Resistance of RC T-beams after Strengthening with Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) Bars

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the stiffness and shear resistance of T-reinforced concrete beams that have been strengthened against shear using the embedded through-section approach. The beams were exposed to a monotonic one-point load until failure. The experimental methodology included the investigation of 12 T beams made of reinforced concrete, consisting of 2 reference beams that were not subjected to any strengthening measures and 10 reinforced beams. The 12 beams were classified into two primary categories: those with stirrups and those without stirrups. The primary factors from each group encompassed the spacing and angle of inclination pertaining to the Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) bars placed along the central axis of the section. Various configurations were used, including varied spacing intervals and degrees of inclination. The results showed that the ratio of the CFRP shear resistance to the total section (V_f / V_{sec}) ranged between 10 to 21% in group one (with stirrups). This means that the Embedded Through Section (ETS) technique with CFRP bars is useful in increasing the shear resistance of reinforced concrete beams. For group two (without stirrups), this ratio ranged between 56 to 58.5%. That is, ETS with CFRP bars significantly increases the shear resistance of reinforced concrete beams without stirrups.

Keywords-shear resistance; stiffness; Embedded Through Section (ETS); CFRP bars; reinforced concrete T-beams

I. INTRODUCTION

During the recent years, there has been a growing interest in the use of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites for reinforcing concrete parts to rehabilitate infrastructure. The use of CFRP reinforcement demonstrates a diverse array of applications, entailing the construction of innovative structures and the rehabilitation of pre-existing ones [1-7]. The shear strength of Reinforced Concrete (RC) beams is influenced by many factors [8-10]. These factors include the compressive strength of the concrete (f_c), the ratio of main steel (ρ), the dimensions of the beam, the ratio of shear span to effective depth (a/d), and the ratio of shear reinforcement (ρ_v). Several studies have attempted to define the bond behavior at the interface where premature failures originate [11-14]. Authors in [15] conducted a thorough analysis and practical study of RC T-beams that were strengthened in shear using Embedded Through-Section (ETS) Fiber-Reinforced Polymer

(FRP). The study examined the impact of various factors on the performance of FRP bars, including the influence of the surface coating on FRP bars, the effect of internal transverse steel reinforcement on FRP shear contribution, the influence of FRP bar spacing, the impact of FRP rod diameter, and the efficiency of the embedded through-section FRP rod method. Novel design equations were introduced to compute the shear contribution of FRP for beams reinforced using the ETS FRP method. The design equations were verified using data obtained from the experimental portion of the present research investigation. The proposed model exhibits a satisfactory correlation with the experimental findings. Authors in [16] examined 14 RC beams strengthened in shear by CFRP textiles bonded with cement-based adhesive CBA. The experimental results demonstrated that the CBA-bonded CFRP textiles substantially enhanced the shear capacity of the RC members. The structural performance of RC columns strengthened in shear with ETS Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) bars

was experimentally and analytically investigated in [17]. The results showed that the configuration and specifics of the anchorage system should be carefully considered before formulating unified specifications. Authors in [18] presented a comprehensive investigation of the shear behavior of the RC beams reinforced with a small-diameter FRP bar-reinforced geopolymer matrix (FRGM) system. The findings indicated that utilizing steel fibers in the geopolymer matrix further inhibited the formation of shear fractures and enhanced shear capacity. Using 18 shear-deficient RC beams strengthened with Near Surface Mounted (NSM) CFRP bars, authors in [19] conducted an experimental analysis to determine the bars impact on the shear strength of the RC beams. The reinforced beams were found to have a shear capacity that was up to 35% higher than that of the control beams. It was also noted that, compared to beams with higher strength concrete, those with standard strength concrete showed a greater increase in shear strength.

According to the literature review, and to the best of our knowledge, no research has been conducted on the shear behavior of reinforced concrete T-beams strengthened by CFRP bars using the ETS technique.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

The experimental program included testing a total of 12 RC T-beams, consisting of 2 reference beams not subjected to any strengthening measures and 10 beams that were strengthened with the ETS Technique with CFRP bars. The 12 beams were classified into 2 primary categories, namely those with stirrups and those without stirrups, with the latter involving just 3 beams for steel bar support. The primary factors under investigation were the CFRP bars' spacing and inclination degree. The reinforced beams exhibited enhanced resistance to shear forces by inserting 12 mm CFRP bars along the beam central axis, using various spacing intervals and inclination degrees. An experimental investigation was carried out to investigate the impact of spacing and inclination angle of CFRP bars on several factors, including failure load, fracture distribution, load-strain relation, and load-deflection relationship. All beams within each group exhibited uniform characteristics, encompassing a consistent length of 2200 mm, exact cross-sectional dimensions, and equivalent reinforcing. The beams in question were exposed to a unidirectional single-point load applied at the midpoint until reaching the point of failure, as seen in Figures 1 and 2. The tested beams were designed according to ACI-318-19 [20] and ACI440-17 [21]. Table I illustrates the configuration and designation of the tested beams.

Concrete's properties, such as its modulus of elasticity, and tensile and compressive strengths, were calculated. The properties of the concrete (after 28 days), CFRP bars, and steel reinforcements employed in this study are illustrated in Table II. Figure 3 shows the ETS shear strengthening technique using CFRP bars, while Figure 4 shows a tested T-beam.

Fig. 1. Details of the beams for group one (with stirrups) (all dimensions in mm): (a) Un-strengthened reference beam, (b) strengthened beam, (c) strengthened beam with inclined CFRP bars.

Fig. 2. Details of the beams for group two without stirrups (just 3 for support) (all dimensions in mm): (a) Un-strengthened reference beam, (b) strengthened beam with vertical CFRP bars, (c) strengthened beam with inclined CFRP bars.

TABLE I. DETAILS OF THE TESTED BEAMS.

Group	Beam-ID	Angle of inclination of CFRP bar (deg.)	CFRP bar spacing (mm)
Group one (with stirrups)	G1-B1-Ref	-	-
	G1-B2-R-S10	90	100
	G1-B3-R-S15	90	150
	G1-B4-R-S20	90	200
	G1-B5-I-S10	45	100
	G1-B6-I-S15	45	150
	G1-B7-I-S20	45	200
Group two (without stirrups)	G2-B1-Ref	-	-
	G2-B2-R-S10	90	100
	G2-B3-R-S15	90	150
	G2-B4-I-S10	45	100
	G2-B5-I-S15	45	150

TABLE II. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Properties	Steel bars		Concrete	CFRP bar (12mm)
	8 mm	25 mm		
Tensile yield (MPa)	522.5	553.8	-	-
Tensile strength (MPa)	661.5	701	3.73	3100
Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	200		28.645	148
Compressive strength (MPa)	-	-	45.3	-

Fig. 3. ETS shear strengthening using CFRP bars.

Fig. 4. A tested T beam.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A comparative analysis was conducted on the test findings and on the reinforced specimens behavior in relation to the control T-beams, both with and without stirrups. The study also examined the impact of the spacing and angle of inclination of the CFRP bars on shear strength.

A. Beam Stiffness (k)

The serviceability limit used for this study was regulated by dividing the experimental ultimate load by a factor of 1.7, a recommendation supported by previous researchers such as [22]. This criterion was applied due to the absence of any unwanted cracking or deformation seen at this particular load level. Tables III and IV provide a comprehensive overview of the tested beams stiffness at the service stage for groups 1 and 2, respectively.

Table III shows that the beams stiffness of group one (with stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacing of 100, 150, and 200 mm increased by 35.6, 22, and 11.9%, respectively. In comparison, the stiffness of the beams of group one with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacing of 100, 150 and 200 mm increased by 50.8, 27, and 17%, accordingly with respect to the reference beam. This finding indicates that the spacing of the CFRP bars is inversely proportional to the beam stiffness for the exact inclination angle. It is also seen that the inclined CFRP bars (45°) perform better than the vertical ones.

TABLE III. STIFFNESS k OF THE BEAMS OF GROUP ONE

Beam ID	At service loading Ps				Failure load (kN)
	Load (kN)	Deflection (mm)	k (kN/mm)	% increase in k	
G1-B1-Ref	265.3	4.5	59	Ref.	451
G1-B2-R-S10	335.3	4.22	80	35.6	570
G1-B3-R-S15	314.7	4.4	72	22	535
G1-B4-R-S20	294.7	4.49	66	11.9	501
G1-B5-I-S10	344.1	3.85	89	50.8	585
G1-B6-I-S15	324.7	4.31	75	27	552
G1-B7-I-S20	306.5	4.45	69	17	521

k=Load/Deflection

TABLE IV. STIFFNESS k OF THE BEAMS OF GROUP TWO

Beam ID	At service loading Ps				Failure load (kN)
	Load (kN)	Deflection (mm)	k (kN/mm)	% increase in k	
G2-B1-Ref	130	2.9	44.8	Ref.	221
G2-B2-R-S10	305.3	4.12	74	65.2	519
G2-B3-R-S15	295.3	4.48	66	47.3	502
G2-B4-I-S10	313	3.8	82.4	84	532
G2-B5-I-S15	300	4.14	72.5	61.8	510

k=Load/Deflection

Table IV shows that the beams stiffness of group two (without stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacing of 100, and 150 mm increased by 65.2 and 47.3%, respectively, while the stiffness of the beams of group two with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacings of 100 and 150 mm augmented by 84 and 61.8%, respectively, concerning the reference beam. This finding shows that the spacing of the CFRP bars is inversely proportional to the beam stiffness for the exact angle of inclination in this group. It is clear that the impact of CFRP bars was more effective on group two than on group one because the beams of group two have no shear stirrups. Figure 5 shows the stiffness of all the beams.

Fig. 5. Stiffness of all the tested beams.

B. Experimental Shear Resistance

The shear resistance of concrete (Vc) was taken as the half of the ultimate load of set two control beam (without stirrups), i.e. G2-B1-REF. While the shear resistance of steel (Vs) was taken as the half of the difference between the ultimate load of the control beam of set two (without stirrups) G2-B1-REF and the set one reference beam (with stirrups) G1-B1-REF. Table V shows the additional shear resistance of CFRP bars (Vf) for each beam. So, the calculated values were:

$$V_c = 0.5 \times 221 = 110.5 \text{ kN}$$

$$V_s = 0.5(451-221) = 115 \text{ kN}$$

$$V_f = V_{sec.} - (V_c + V_s) \dots\dots (1)$$

$$V_{sec.} = 0.5 \times P_u \text{ (for each beam)} (2)$$

TABLE V. SHEAR RESISTANCE OF THE TESTED BEAMS.

Group	Specimens	Ultimate load	Vsec (kN)	Vc (kN)	Vs (kN)	Gain attributable to CFRP (%)	Vf (kN)	Vf / Vsec. (%)	Vf / Vc (%)
Group1	G1-B1-Ref	451	225.5	110.5	115	Ref.	-	-	-
	G1-B2-R-S10	570	285	110.5	115	26.39	59.5	21	54
	G1-B3-R-S15	535	267.5	110.5	115	18.6	42	16	38
	G1-B4-R-S20	501	250.5	110.5	115	11.1	25	10	27
	G1-B5-I-S10	585	292.5	110.5	115	29.7	67	23	61
	G1-B6-I-S15	552	276	110.5	115	22.4	50.5	18.3	46
	G1-B7-I-S20	521	260.5	110.5	115	15.5	35	13.4	32
Group2	G2-B1-Ref	221	110.5	110.5	-	Ref.	-	-	-
	G2-B2-R-S10	519	259.5	110.5	-	135	149	57.4	135
	G2-B3-R-S15	502	251	110.5	-	127	140.5	56	127
	G2-B4-I-S10	532	266	110.5	-	141	155.5	58.5	141
	G2-B5-I-S15	510	255	110.5	-	131	144.5	56.7	131

Table V shows that the ultimate beams load of group one (with stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacings of 100, 150, and 200 mm increased by 26.39, 18.6, and 11.1%, respectively. On the contrary, the beams stiffness of group one with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacings of 100, 150, and 200 mm increased by 29.7, 22.4, and 15.5%, respectively, with regard to the reference beam. This suggests that there is an inverse relationship between the spacing of the CFRP bars and the ultimate load of the beam, specifically for the given inclination angle. Furthermore, this discovery suggests that inclined CFRP bars at 45° have superior performance compared to the vertical bars. Table V also shows that the ultimate load of the group tow beams (without stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacings of 100 and 150 mm grew by 135 and 127%, respectively. The stiffness of group two beams, with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacings of 100 and 150 mm, though, increased by 141 and 131%, correspondingly, regarding the reference beam. This finding indicates that the increasing spacing of the CFRP bars is inversely proportional to the beam stiffness for the exact angle of inclination in this group. It is clear that CFRP bars presence was more effective in group two than in group one because group two beams have no shear stirrups. Figures 6 to 17 describe the failure mechanism and fracture patterns of every single T-beam.

Fig. 7. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B2-R-S10.

Fig. 8. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B3-R-S15.

Fig. 6. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B1-REF.

Fig. 9. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B4-R-S20.

Fig. 10. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B5-I-S10.

Fig. 14. Failure crack pattern of specimen G2-B2-R-S10.

Fig. 11. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B6-I-S15.

Fig. 15. Failure crack pattern of specimen G2-B3-R-S15.

Fig. 12. Failure crack pattern of specimen G1-B7-I-S20.

Fig. 16. Failure crack pattern of specimen G2-B4-I-S10.

Fig. 13. Failure crack pattern of specimen G2-B1-REF.

Fig. 17. Failure crack pattern of specimen G2-B5-I-S15.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates two essential properties of the RC beam, i.e. stiffness and shear resistance, because these

properties give a good indicator of the RC beams shear behavior after strengthening with CFRP bars. Based on the experimental results, we can obtain the following conclusions:

- The stiffness of group one beams (with stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacing of 100, 150, and 200 mm increased by 35.6, 22, and 11.9%, respectively, whereas the stiffness of group one beams with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacing of 100, 150, and 200 mm rose by 50.8, 27, and 17%, correspondingly, with regard to the reference beam. It is concluded that CFRP bars spacing is inversely proportional to the beam stiffness for the exact inclination angle.
- The inclined CFRP bars (45°) perform better than the vertical ones.
- The stiffness of group two beams (without stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacing of 100 and 150 mm increased by 65.2, and 47.3%, accordingly, whereas the stiffness of group two beams with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacing of 100 and 150 mm increased by 84 and 61.8%, respectively. The CFRP bars influence was more effective on group two than group one because group two beams have no shear stirrups.
- The ultimate load of group one beams (with stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacing of 100, 150, and 200 mm augmented by 26.39, 18.6, and 11.1%, respectively, whereas the stiffness of group one beams with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacing of 100, 150, and 200 mm increased by 29.7, 22.4, and 15.5 %, correspondingly, with regard to the reference beam. This suggests an inverse relationship between the CFRP bars spacing and the ultimate load of the beam, specifically for the given inclination angle.
- Inclined CFRP bars at a 45° angle perform better than vertical bars.
- The ultimate load of group two beams (without stirrups) with vertical CFRP bars and spacing of 100 and 150 mm increased by 135, and 127%, respectively, whereas the stiffness of group two beams with inclined CFRP bars (45°) and spacing of 100 and 150 mm rose by 141 and 131%, respectively with regard to the reference beam.
- The ratio of the CFRP shear resistance to concrete (V_f / V_c) ranged between 27 to 61% in group one (with stirrups). For group two (without stirrups), this ratio ranged between 1.27 to 1.41%.
- The ratio of the CFRP shear resistance to the total section (V_f / V_{sec}) ranged between 10 to 21% in group one (with stirrups). This means that the ETS technique with CFRP bars is useful in increasing the shear resistance of RC beams. For group two (without stirrups), this ratio ranged between 56 to 58.5%, which means that ETS with CFRP bars significantly increases the shear resistance of RC beams without stirrups.

Recommendations for future research work: Investigation of the behavior of strengthened T-RC beams with CFRP bars

under repeated load and studying the behavior of prestressed strengthened T-reinforced concrete beams with CFRP bars.

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Classified Volatile Organic Compound Detection using Data Classification Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

Sensors are becoming smaller and less expensive, sparking interest in assessing vast volumes of sensor data. Meanwhile, the emergence of machine learning has led to the development of technologies that have a substantial impact on our lives. Machine learning models are often used to produce accurate, real-time predictions even in the presence of noisy sensed data. In this study, a Volatile Organic Compound (VOC) categorization system based on sensor data collected from a sensor array was developed. The most difficult challenge posed in the sensor array was the detection of the type of VOC. It is feasible to categorize VOCs brought on by applying data classification algorithms to data collected from sensor devices. In this work, we used data from the classification algorithms Decision Tree (DT), Naive Bayes (NB), and Linear Regression (LR) on a developed linear sensor array and their classification accuracy was compared. Four different VOCs were evaluated: acetone (C_3H_6O), benzene (C_6H_6), ethanol (C_2H_5OH), and toluene ($C_6H_5CH_3$). The acquired classification accuracy reached 95.65% with the LR algorithm.

Keywords-cantilever; classified detection; MEMS; machine learning; sensor; VOC

I. INTRODUCTION

Sensor system applications growth in a variety of fields, including conservation and development, climate motoring, and anthropogenic detection, has been made possible, to a substantial degree, by developments that have taken place over the years, specifically in recent times. It is common knowledge that sensor-based systems are application-dependent [1]. This also comprises the top part, which is responsible for handling the data in an effective and constructive approach. As the number and scale of deployed sensor networks rises, so does the amount of data gathered, necessitating the use of specialized methodologies that can handle this scale while still meeting application requirements. In this research, the authors demonstrate how sophisticated Machine Learning (ML) algorithms [2] might be utilized to analyze autonomously obtained sensor data in conjunction with manually gathered data in order to make predictions for a diversity of occurrences. Our presentation is based on the data acquired from an array-modeled sensor that was designed and developed for detection of most hazardous Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) [3]. This research concentrates on ML and data mining for the interpretation of sensor data as a component of comprehensive system integration. This implementation ranges from hardware at the bottom level all the way up to data-driven ML algorithms at the topmost level. The proposed system is an example of

applying ML methods on sensor data, which can provide high-level guidelines for similar applications and involve predictions based on sensor data.

II. RELATED WORK

The number of vertical system implementations is not very large, but a similar research was conducted in [4]. The authors describe a networked sensor architecture designed to enable human interaction. This architecture is made up of equipment often found in an office setting, such as personal computers, Personal Digital Assistants (PDAs), telephones, etc. In order to construct the training set, each activity observed by the monitoring devices must first be manually labeled. This strategy is different from the one we've been using in terms of the sensors involved. Instead of a vertical system, the focus is given on the Bayesian learning approach. Table I shows a review of the recent literature on VOC detection. The research in [12] pertains to technology implementation in sensor nodes. Sensor data are modeled for queries in a variety of contexts via the use of RDF (Resource Description Framework) and RDQL (RDF Data Query Language) query languages, with a few tweaks here and there. In spite of this, the dataset was acquired by simulating a sensor network, which highlights the system performance as well as the programming language. Because of this, the system performance in a real-time environment may

differ. An alternative technique is presented in [13, 14], in which all the detection systems are modeled employing Dynamic Conditional Random Fields (DCRFs) to evaluate the

real-world, in which sensor information may be distorted, impacted by noise, or lost. This allows for a more accurate representation of the environment [15, 16].

TABLE I. LITERATURE REVIEW

Year	Reference	Methodology	Application	Limitation
1998	[5]	MEMS cantilever arrays with functionalized coatings	Environmental monitoring, industrial safety	Limited selectivity, cross-sensitivity to other compounds
2007	[6]	MEMS cantilevers combined with gas chromatography	Air quality assessment, chemical process control	Complex setup, expensive instrumentation
2010	[7]	MEMS cantilever arrays with nanomaterial functionalization	Indoor air quality, breath analysis	Short functionalization lifespan, drift over time
2013	[8]	Multiple MEMS cantilevers with differential readout	Indoor air quality, leak detection	Cross-sensitivity to humidity, temperature variations
2016	[9]	MEMS cantilever arrays with integrated microheaters	Environmental monitoring, explosive detection	Energy consumption, slow response time
2019	[10]	Compact MEMS cantilever array-based sensor	Personal exposure monitoring, wearable devices	Limited dynamic range, potential interference from background odors
2022	[11]	MEMS cantilevers with machine learning algorithms	Smart buildings, precision agriculture	Data interpretation challenges, need for continuous calibration

III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 demonstrates the system components, which are: the sensors and actuators, a server for collecting sensor data, a humanoid element that is instrumental in developing extra data, a database that contains the additional data, data preparation tools, and a ML toolbox. In order to collect the dataset, we must first get the raw data from the sensor array that are located on the sensor node, and then send this data to a computer so as to be stored. In the next step, we will combine the automatically collected data with the data labeled by hand so that the ML algorithms can be trained using the pre-processing techniques.

Fig. 1. Basic components of the proposed system.

As per the characteristics of fabricated sensor [17], Figure 2 shows that the computer is wired to the RS232 to USB converter, which is a part of the integrated sensor network. The sensor node also includes a 3 V power supply, display screen, and an ATmega328P microcontroller. When the sensor is exposed to respective reactants, a reaction takes place on cantilever surface and provides output voltage. Then, the microcontroller collects data from the integrated sensors at a sample rate of 500 ms, packs the data into a vector, and then transmits them to a server through the serial connection so that it will be possible for them to be retained. The data may also be observed via a serial monitor.

During the course of the research, the collected data were kept in a word document, with each sample including a time

stamp along with the numerical values obtained from the sensor array. Each time sensor array is able to identify one of the 4 VOCs but the user does know the exact classifier from the range of the output values. This issue is tackled by introducing data classifiers between the sensor output and the system display. Minimum, maximum, and mean values of the sensor data are shown in Table II, for all 4 VOCs in terms of resistance change of the cantilever surface. The values have not significant differences. Since there are no extreme results, it is possible to say that the observations are correct.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup to identify resistance range of the array cantilever: (a) Cantilever deflection when its is exposed to VOC, (b) encapsulated cantilever, (c) practical setup interfaced with the system, (d) terminal output.

TABLE II. MINIMUM AND MAXIMUM VALUES OF RESISTANCE CHANGE FOR EACH VOC

VOC	Min.	Max.	Mean
Acetone (C_3H_6O)	53.3 K Ω	53.6 K Ω	53.4 K Ω
Benzene (C_6H_6)	55.2 K Ω	55.8 K Ω	55.6 K Ω
Ethanol (C_2H_5OH)	56.4 K Ω	56.6 K Ω	56.5 K Ω
Toluene ($C_6H_5CH_3$)	55.5 K Ω	55.9 K Ω	55.7 K Ω

The illustration of a scenario showing the way sensor data progressed in the laboratory during the period of experimentation is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that when the integrated sensor was exposed to the reactants, after the

transient state, the values increased with time and became steady after a few seconds. This can be noticed in Figure 3(a), representing the sensor response in the idle case. A negative transient indicates fluctuation due to surge voltage when the power is ON. With respect to time, it becomes stable in the steady state.

Fig. 3. Response of the array cantilever from the initial state to the steady state. (a) Idle sensor, (b) sensor exposed to a proportional reactant, (c) response of the sensor from the transient to the steady state, (d) steady state response of a sensor with a significant change in amplitude.

Figure 3(b) depicts the result of a sensor exposed to a proportional reactant. Significant reaction takes place between the analyte and the reactant, and as the sensor is more sensitive in nature, a few glitches occurred in the transient state. Figure 3(c) illustrates the sensor response from the transient to the steady state. The observed glitches have low frequencies. Similarly, Figure 3(d) shows the steady state sensor response with significant change in amplitude.

A. Data Processing and Learning

In the first stage of data processing, sensor information and physically obtained data were aligned using time. The initial sampling rate for the sensor information was set to 500 ms, whereas the time stamp for the physically obtained data was simply included with the hours and minutes of the input. We allocated the matching instance from the extra acquired sensor data occurred within the same minute for each cantilever sensor of the array modelled sensor. So, given that time stamps on the manually gathered data are only in HH:MM:SS format, the second step was to reduce the dimensionality problem. The first thing we did was to choose a sample rate of 100 ms. However, several sensor data characteristics, such as the non-clean room ambient environment (light intensity, air pressure, and dust particulates), show significant fluctuations over the instant of experimentation, and these variations cannot be accurately correlated with any other data. The time stamps from the two different data sources may differ by a few seconds due to the fact that extra data were added by a greater number of samples and no time synchronization was performed. We also removed data based on the difference of successive samples collected throughout the experimentation, since this enabled us to avoid having an excessive number of redundant samples. To be more specific, the data collected throughout the experiment did not include any repeated values, and thus incorporating all these data would have resulted in an extremely imbalanced dataset. Due to the fact that it is impossible to precisely correlate sensor data with manually gathered data and that humans make mistakes, the produced dataset includes some inaccurate occurrences. On the other hand, there are no gaps in the data and no missing values in the dataset.

The learning process utilized a dataset that contained a total of 20286 measurements, each of which has 6 attributes: Deflection, stress, change in resistance, temperature, moisture, ambient pressure. We used two different learning methods, i.e. classification and regression. The first technique is applied for the prediction of classified class labels, while the second approach approximates the target variable by modeling a continuous-valued function (class attribute). Since the target variable in our context might be interpreted both as a discrete-valued variable and as a numerical variable, we came to the conclusion that it would be best to evaluate both approaches. DT and the NB classifiers were used as classification techniques. The first one offers a clear visual explanation of the findings, whereas the second one makes more effective use of the characteristics of the dataset as a whole. We decided to go with the standard method of LR for regression analysis [18].

IV. RESULT INTERPRETATION AND EVALUATION

Aiming to test the predictive capability of each method, we ran experiments on two different datasets: one with just sensor data characteristics (deflection Voltage, change in resistance, stress, and ambient pressure) and the other with a class attribute with extra arbitrarily inserted input. Two distinct ML algorithms were chosen to classify data: the J48 algorithm for learning DTs and NB allowed us to evaluate how various learning approaches performed on the datasets. For the regression data analysis, we used a procedure known as conventional LR. The WEKA toolbox [19] provided the execution of these computations. It is necessary to examine how well the algorithms worked with both the basic and its supplemented dataset. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) were engaged to measure how accurate the forecasts are. Although MAE and RMSE give more emphasis on how significant the disparity between the expected and observed values is, the classification accuracy was additionally provided for each classification method.

A. Decision Tree

After conducting a number of initial experiments, we decided to implement the limitation that representation must include at least 10% of the total number of instances. All these DTs [20] feature the cantilever deflection response measurements property in the cluster head. This allows for simple classification of a huge observations set when sensors exposed to other than the specified VOCs lead to a low value (less than or equal to 56.7 K). The sensor's cantilever resistance change and output voltage are the two parameters utilized for categorization when looking at the basic dataset. Additionally, the topology of the DT was altered as a result of new data input. In this case, only one piece of the new data is used, which is the total number of computers that are working. Considering data overfitting, we chose the Naive Bayesian learning approach [21, 22]. This method employs probability distribution over a set of variables. If the minimum number of occurrences in a branch is raised, it could lead to data overfitting.

B. The Bayesian Network

In an attempt to implement the Naive Bayesian method, we configured the WEKA toolkit with the settings of simple estimator and K2 search algorithm. Tables III-IV provide the confusion matrices for two distinct scenarios involving simple and enhanced datasets. In the case of the supplemented dataset, there is a clearer contrast between occurrences that include zero deflection response and the instances that contain more than non-zero deflection response. When considering the class property to have only two possible values—Zero (0) and Non-Zero ($\neq 0$) (in terms of the response), we are able to determine whether or not our system is suitable for VOC detection. We carried out Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). The results demonstrated increased predictive performance on the supplemented dataset up to 86.52%, in contrast to the 84% of the cases properly identified when there were 4 categories (class attribute values). The findings are shown in Table V, which also includes a representation of the cost and confusion matrices.

TABLE III. CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE SIMPLE DATASET

	0	1	2	3
0	7096	120	100	11
1	95	2988	891	218
2	37	833	2566	253
3	1	246	492	640

TABLE IV. CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE AUGMENTED DATASET

	0	1	2	3
0	7073	208	45	1
1	38	3085	933	173
2	0	557	2731	401
3	0	16	378	985

TABLE V. COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Cost Matrix		0	1	Confusion Matrix	0	1
	0	0.0	1.0		7018	250
	1	5.0	0.0		21	8045
Acc.	86.52%					

C. Linear Regression

A quite uncomplicated LR algorithm [23-25] was employed. As a result, each response property in the supplemented dataset was converted to 3 binary characteristics (with values of 0 or 1) pertaining to each of the nominal values.

From Tables VI-VIII, the accuracy of 95.65% indicates that the model is performing extraordinarily well. According to the cost matrix, false negatives (1 misclassified as 0) have a larger cost than false positives (0 misclassified as 1). This indicates that the model has been optimized to minimize false negatives, which may be appropriate for applications where missing a positive instance is more expensive. The confusion matrix reveals that there are much more true positives (9156) than false positives (290), exhibiting that the model is performing well in properly detecting positive events. There are also much more true negatives (7256) than false negatives (28), indicating that the binary classification model is working well. The resultant linear model that will be utilized for prediction is depicted in Figure 4(a). On the supplemented data, the features with the highest coefficients are the appropriate sensor responses, displaying that these factors have a favorable influence on the decisions that can be anticipated. As mentioned above, the model has a very high overall accuracy of 95.65%. Understanding the specific domain and application context (sensor environment), on the other hand, is crucial in assessing if these levels of accuracy and misclassification costs are appropriate. The trade-off between false positives and false negatives is determined by the application's specific goals and requirements. The model works well, especially when it comes to correctly categorizing positive occurrences. The cost matrix was selected with the intention of reducing false negatives.

Three machine learning models (DT, NB, and LR) were tested on two datasets, i.e. Simple and Augmented (Table IX). For all models, the augmented dataset outperforms the simple dataset, indicating that more data or new attributes improve the prediction accuracy and reduce errors. LR outperforms the other ML models in both datasets, with NB coming second. LR

yields the highest accuracy, whereas NB yields the lowest MAE and RMSE values. It should be noted that further fine-tuning may increase performance.

TABLE VI. CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE SIMPLE DATASET

	0	1	2	3
0	8093	302	52	2
1	48	3086	895	183
2	0	568	2731	411
3	0	19	478	980

TABLE VII. CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE AUGMENTED DATASET

	0	1	2	3
0	8096	150	120	12
1	95	3988	903	260
2	36	560	2831	453
3	1	18	522	680

TABLE VIII. COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Cost Matrix				Confusion Matrix		
	0	1	2		0	1
	0.0	1.0		7256	290	
	5.0	0.0		28	9156	
Acc.	95.65%					

Fig. 4. (a) Classification report of the test data, (b) classified output from the modeled biosensor array.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, we introduced a hierarchical system integration method for VOC classification based on sensor

results. We created an augmented dataset by labelling sensor data with additional data, and then used machine learning algorithms to learn from that dataset. The examination of the obtained predicted results from both the basic and the enriched datasets proved that effective VOC classification can be forecast when using sensor data. The prediction can be improved by giving any of the three machine learning techniques new information. The application and the anticipated results have a role in the decision of which machine learning algorithm to apply. On the basis of our data, in comparison with decision trees and Naive Bayes, linear regression produce better results, however, more trials on larger datasets are needed to draw definitive conclusions.

This study findings are promising for the continuous development of the system, which will include the creation of a network of sensors in order to get more information. Also, the possibility of adding semantic technologies to the current system to enhance the data and make predictions both of which will be more accurate and more varied will be examined.

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A Numerical Analysis on the Performance and Optimization of the Savonius Wind Turbine for Agricultural Use

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ABSTRACT

Given the state of the world nowadays, renewable energy is becoming more and more essential rendering wind turbine electricity quite important. Its shape and the fact that the Savonius vertical axis wind turbine runs at relatively low wind speeds with high torque values makes it suitable for practical uses such as that of an irrigation system in agriculture industry. This paper utilizes numerical research with Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to investigate the performance of a vertical-axis wind turbine. The ANSYS CFD program was engaged to construct the simulations during the pre- and post-processing stages. Wind speed remained constant while the angular velocity was altered to enable analysis of the flow through the wind turbine. Because of its mechanical simplicity, the primary profile of a semicircle has remained a typical option for turbines that generate high torque based on drag force. The effects of using elliptical curves and the fluctuation in thickness along the profile chord were both examined in this study. Equivalently, an attempt to optimize the rotor's design was made. After the performance of a numerical simulation, a geometry consisting of simple circle arcs was developed, with a 10.9% improvement in the power coefficient, analogous to prior optimizations with more complicated geometries. The numerical results derived include the torque coefficient evolution throughout a full rotation as well as the distribution of vorticity magnitude at different rotor points.

Keywords-renewable energy; VAWT; Savonius; CFD; power coefficient; TSR

I. INTRODUCTION

The need to continue tackling global problems regarding climate change and resource consumption is critical in the current socioeconomic environment. Therefore, the main component of the proposed United Nations resolution to achieve zero net carbon emissions by 2050 is renewable energy. With the potential to cover 35% of the world's future energy needs, wind energy plays a significant part in the attempt to accomplish a sustainable future [1]. During the last year, new installations producing 19 GW of electricity have been established, bringing the total amount of wind energy generated in Europe to 255 GW and so reinforcing the continent's current efforts to meet its energy and climate goals.

Despite appearing to be a respectable quantity, the produced wind energy amount falls short of the target to obtain up to 451 GW by 2030, necessitating an increase of more than 50% in the yearly wind energy production [2].

Agricultural industry has been continuously on an expansion mode and thus it can be assumed that the pollution created by generating the required energy can have a negative impact on the climate change crisis [3]. Consequently, renewable energy applications demonstrate a major potential in this sector. Given the growth of wind energy use over the past ten years, it is reasonable to draw the conclusion from an economic viewpoint that using a power source based on wind is similar to using a typical source based on fossil fuel from a

cost-effective standpoint [4]. In this light, utilizing wind turbine technology efficiently to generate power would be ideal for decreasing carbon emissions in agriculture [5]. One operation that might be benefited by wind turbine usage is irrigation. That is, the required power for pumping can be reached by using vertical wind turbines under typical operating conditions [7]. Additionally, as the power comes straight from the shaft [6], there are no conversion losses in this situation as opposed to other systems, adding another advantageous technological aspect.

In general, Vertical-Axis Wind Turbines (VAWTs) [8] are more desirable than horizontal-axis turbines because they are functional and efficient with relatively modest design parameters and can be used on a smaller scale [9]. Their simpler operation and usage, compared to horizontal turbines, their ability to function in all wind directions and their easier maintenance make VAWTs more preferable. Taking into consideration the fact that developing countries are in a struggle to implement renewable energy due to technical and financial reasons [10], it would be appropriate to choose a small VAWT with a low level of technological complexity such as the Savonius one. In this direction, throughout the recent decades there have been some isolated instances where wind energy produced by a Savonius turbine type was used successfully in agriculture in developing countries such as Peru or Indonesia [11]. More recently there have been studies effectuated to implement wind energy sources to suitable regions in South Africa [12]. In comparison to the other VAWT types, the Savonius type performs better when it starts operating with lower wind speeds [13]. The profile section is made up of two semicircular profiles with an S-shaped appearance that are projected at an angle on the z-axis to improve the behavior of the turbulent flow. It has been shown that 180° is the ideal angle of twist for a two-bladed, single-stage Savonius [14]. This offers the fundamental benefit of technological simplicity in addition to its compact size.

A procedure to extract the greatest potential from a device whose movement is dependent on drag force has not yet been acknowledged by a significant group of specialists; therefore, there is a constant quest for these devices optimization based on diverse points of view [15]. One approach to solving this issue is to primarily focus on the negative torque produced and attempt to reduce it. In this regard, a few studies have used deflectors [16], barrier plates [17], or a curtain design [18], even though these may have limitations in terms of capturing all of the wind's potential energy. In addition to studying how to manipulate the flow using exterior structures, there are optimizations involving key design elements like the aforementioned aspect and overlap ratio, twist angle, and the influence that the number of stages and blades has on them [19-21]. Going into elliptical geometry, altering the blades thickness along the chord or the blade arc angle, and more recently, a blade design modeled from sand eels, can all be noted as enhancements to the section's geometry [22]. A common way in these optimization methods is to employ a genetic algorithm [23], where the inferred condition is checked using CFD during the iteration step. This process has become important and typical in experimental research concerning flow characteristics or aerodynamic analysis as an extra method of

validation and a more analytical approach to streamline behavior [24].

The Savonius wind turbine flow is typically modeled as 2D flow in CFD studies, which is similar to the mid-plane flow of the rotor's turbine [25, 26]. The Savonius power performance estimation has something of an upper bound in the shape of the 2D prediction. This method is useful since it requires less computational time and resources to run the numerous CFD simulations necessary for rotor geometry optimization. In contrast to 3D analysis results [27] or even to experiments outcomes [28-29], 2D unsteady CFD simulations, typically overestimate the torque, and the peak of the torque coefficient versus tip speed ratio curve is shifted to a higher TSR.

Unsteady 2D simulations on an improved design of a traditional Savonius wind turbine were performed in this paper using the ANSYS Fluent CFD to examine the aerodynamic performance and forces acting on this type of wind turbine. Six operating points were studied for this work in order to assess the turbine flow behavior. In the future, the numerical results derived from the computational model will be validated in an experimental testing program which will be conducted in a wind tunnel.

II. METHODOLOGY

The geometry of the typical Savonius rotor has certain features when it comes to its design [30]. In order to find out the height, rotor diameter, chord of the blade and other geometric variables it is initially needed to set a core of logical concepts related to wind turbines. The principle from which the calculations begin is based on the necessary power output, where the turbine application is a good indicator to assume a certain value. Another set parameter is the power coefficient C_p which describes similarly to an efficiency factor how much power is actually harvested. According to [31] a proper value for the Savonius type is 0.15. Subsequently it is defined as:

$$C_p = \frac{P_0}{P_w} \quad (1)$$

where P_0 is the power that gets generated by the turbine and P_w the potential power of the wind [30]. They can be expressed as:

$$P_0 = T\omega \quad (2)$$

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho S V^3 \quad (3)$$

where T is the turbine torque, ω the rotational speed, ρ the air density, S the reference area (in our case, the turbine's diameter multiplied by the turbine's height), and V is the wind velocity.

Setting a constant standard value for the wind speed of 12 m/s and knowing the air density (1.22 kg/m^3), assisted the determination of the turbine swept area, and the geometric feature presented in Table I.

With the help of (2) and (3) in pursuance of improving the design-simulation process and to be able to analyze the numerical simulations results, a further formulation of C_p and with the expression for torque gets:

$$C_p = \frac{\omega R}{V} C_m \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{v} \tag{5}$$

where C_m is the coefficient of torque and the tip speed ratio λ (TSR) is defined as above, representing the connection between the performance of a wind turbine and its aerodynamic characteristics. By having constant the radius and the wind speed, a variation of the angular velocity is needed for the power coefficient analysis. With this equation, it is possible to easily establish C_p through simulations by extracting the aerodynamic torque.

Furthermore, in order to enhance performance, an optimization study has been established. Multiple approaches are considered for this process while techniques to combine them are also under investigation. Instead of going for an implementation of a remote object in the flow and trying to manipulate the torque generation the finding of a geometry that can provide better results is examined.

As Figure 1 shows, there will be a total of 4 arcs for a blade, each with its own parameters. To remain at a stable and simple analysis of the configuration, the center of every arc is situated on the same vertical axis that contains the intersection point of the arcs and the value of the chord remains the same. For a simpler understanding the notations x and y for the horizontal and vertical distances previously discussed are used.

Fig. 1. Savonius 3D model, (b) baseline cross section, (c) optimized geometry cross section.

Figure 1 (a) depicts a 3D CAD model of a twist Savonius wind turbine composed of a pole (1) on which stands the permanent magnetic generator (2), which is coupled to the blades (5) and their end-plates (4) through the shaft (3).

TABLE I. GEOMETRY FEATURES OF SAVONIUS ROTOR

Parameter	Value	
	Baseline	Optimized geometry
Design Power [W]	2000	
D [m]	3	
H [m]	4.5	
c [m]	1.624	
e [m]	0.254	
x_1 [m]	0.812	0.541
x_2 [m]	0.812	1.083
y_1 [m]	0.812	0.438
y_2 [m]	0.812	0.65

As it can be noticed, for each side of the blade the y is equal for both arcs, so y_1 designates the upper side and y_2 the lower side. For x , the first type of arcs for both sides shares the same value x_1 corresponding to the first type of arc and x_2 to the second. Since the sum of x_1 and x_2 has to be the length of the chord, their ratio with the chord determines how close to the elliptical one the geometry will be. Contemplating the ratios between x and y already fixed, a distribution of a third and two thirds of the chord gives with an estimated measure of the reference angle a peak difference of seven degrees from the optimal value of 47.5° . The assessment of the optimal ratios of 0.8 for the lower side and 0.54 for the upper side requires a certain y value for every x . If by the new geometry definition, a common value of y for each side of the blade is established, then an uncertainty concerning to what x to refer when applying the certain ratios appears. For this problem a middle way solution was used, where the horizontal for these ratios is neither x_1 nor x_2 but their average, which is the half of the chord, as shown in Figure 2 where every x and y are expressed by the length c . With this parameterization form, it is obvious that for the base geometry, the x and y values are all equal to the radius of a semicircle, which is equal to the half of the chord.

To check the overall flow behavior and to ensure that the numerical calculations are valid, the spatial domain must be expanded using a multiplier factor based on the rotor diameter. As shown in Figure 4, an inner domain (with the function of the rotor) and an outer domain (with the role of the stator) are specified. After being able to implement the geometry in a CAD program, the next step in the preprocessing stage is to generate the mesh (Figure 3). To achieve high quality, cell sizing criteria are employed for the interface between the inner and outer domains, as well as for the blades, with an inflation command applied to the boundary layer zone.

The cell size was related to the Reynolds number, which remained in the lower portion of the turbulent flow interval. More specifically, we set a characteristic parameter y^+ to an essential value of 1. The cell dimension for the profile's boundary layer may be conditioned and set as the height of the first layer is 0.03 mm and for the sizing of the blades an element size of 5 mm.

To adequately analyze how the grid density can impact the results precision, three cases of number of cells (150000, 200000, and 250000 cells) have been taken into consideration. Therefore, the variation noticed between them has the order of a tenth of a percent. Moreover, given the fact that the time needed to compute the different meshes is somehow proportional to the cells number (reaching even double the time for 250000 cells compared to 150000 cells), the impact is not great enough in order to maintain the simulation efficiency regarding the computation time. A schematic overview of the entire numerical investigation procedure is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Block diagram.

TABLE II. MESH STATISTICS

No.	Subdomain	No. of nodes	No. of elements	
			Tri	Quad
Mesh 1.	Rotor	50871	106	49603
	Stator	103718	35	102864
	TOTAL	154589	152613	
Mesh 2.	Rotor	51280	137	49988
	Stator	150942	22	149962
	TOTAL	202222	200109	
Mesh 3.	Rotor	51954	125	50664
	Stator	201544	34	200433
	TOTAL	253498	251256	

Fig. 3. Rotor's domain mesh.

It has been shown that the $k-\omega$ Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model of the Savonius rotor adequately reflects the real-life phenomenon [32, 33]. Menter's model has the benefit of predicting behavior near the wall as well as away from the surface [34] by integrating the conventional models $k-\omega$ and $k-$

ϵ . This integration is facilitated by a function that links the models by taking different values at various sections of the flow. The governing equations revolve around the kinetic energy (k) and the dissipation rate (ω). In pursuance of a converged solution, each simulation is made with a time span of ten full rotations of the rotor. In order to preserve a strong correlation between the findings and time, the numerical solution's timestep is precisely selected to allow the rotor to revolve by one angular degree during the course of one timestep. With the imposed rotor angular velocity taken into account, the necessary value for this may be calculated with ease.

Fig. 4. Boundary conditions and outer domain features.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A particular variation of C_m with the rotating angle θ is found after running many simulations in Ansys Fluent. Given that torque is produced during motion, both positive and negative, with the magnitude of each varying with the rotating angle, it is reasonable to assume that this type of relationship between an angle and a waveform graph—more precisely, a sine wave with two maxima and two minima with nearly equal values between them—would result. In Figure 5 the torque coefficient for both cases for the last complete 360° revolution is represented. Vorticity magnitude is a crucial parameter in wind turbine CFD simulations that helps study and comprehend the airflow behavior around turbine blades. The local spinning of fluid particles inside a flow field is measured as vorticity. It is useful in determining the air's rotational speed as it flows through or around the blades of a wind turbine.

The Savonius wind turbine is a VAWT well-known for its adaptability to many wind conditions, including low wind speeds. Utilizing the vorticity created by the wind as it passes over the bent blades is one of the fundamental ideas underlying the Savonius turbine's functioning. In the context of a Savonius wind turbine, the strength or intensity of the vortices produced by the revolving blades is referred to as the vorticity magnitude (Figure 6). In essence, the vortices are whirling masses of air created by the blade shapes. The turbine's rotational speed, the turbine's blade size and shape, and the wind speed all have an impact on the vorticity magnitude.

Fig. 5. The torque coefficient variation for the last complete revolution: (a) baseline, (b) optimized geometry.

Fig. 6. Vorticity contours: case 1: (a) 0°, (b) 45°, (c) 90°, (d) 135°, case 2: (a') 0°, (b') 45°, (c') 90°, (d') 135°.

Fig. 7. Power coefficient variation.

A power coefficient (Figure 8) study is also necessary to determine how productive and suitable the model recommended for its application is. A data set of C_p and a dependence on TSR may be visualized with the help of an averaged torque coefficient and the established value of TSR for each numerical calculation. The final TSR range was set to be 0.6–1.8 in order to emphasize the nominal situations for each geometry (1.2 for the base and 1.5 for the new optimized design). These cases are emphasized when the highest values of C_p are obtained (0.319 for the base and 0.371 for the optimized design).

Fig. 8. 3D PLA print of the Savonius model.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Given the dynamic nature of energy, the Savonius wind turbine has favorable traits for agricultural applications and meets the necessary performance benchmarks. By implementing a design that responds to the necessary operating conditions and by utilizing numerical simulations to observe the flow behavior, this might be examined. Moreover, this research delves deeper into the 2D optimization procedures. It thus creates a new geometry that more succinctly combines two previously proven techniques, yielding a notable improvement of 10.9% in comparison to the baseline geometry's nominal case and 28.48% in comparison to the optimized geometry's nominal case. In this sense, the next measures which will be

taken to enhance and catch up to the other wind turbines' performance are straightforward.

Regarding future work, in an effort to capture the flow behavior, the beginning process for various wind speed values will be numerically investigated in both 2D and 3D. Future work will also include an experimental testing campaign which will be conducted in a wind tunnel on smaller models (Figure 8). The final models will be produced using 3D printing technology.

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An Artificial Intelligence Framework for Disease Detection in Potato Plants

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ABSTRACT

Agricultural products are a fundamental necessity for every country. When plants are afflicted with diseases, it influences the country's agricultural productivity, as well as its economic resources. Diseases are an important problem for potato plants, causing potatoes to be rejected and resulting in financial losses. Viruses and diseases in potatoes and field plants can be missed with the naked eye, particularly in the early stages of cultivation. The use of modern instruments and technology at an early stage of disease diagnosis dramatically reduces costs. This study used deep learning techniques to categorize and detect plant leaf diseases in photos taken from the Plant Village dataset. The dataset consists of 20,636 photos of plants and their diseases. This study focused on potato plants because it is the most common type of plant in the world, particularly in Pakistan. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) methods were used to categorize plant leaf diseases into 15 classes, including three classes for healthy leaves and classes for several plant diseases such as fungal and bacterial infections, among others. The proposed models were trained and tested, achieving 98.29 and 98.029% accuracy, respectively.

Keywords-deep learning; disease classification; CNN; potato disease detection; image processing; machine vision; smart sprayer

I. INTRODUCTION

More than a billion people eat potatoes every day as a staple food, making them an important root and tuber crop on a global scale. According to the Uzbekistan State Statistics Committee, Pakistan became the main potato supplier in

January 2022, making approximately 51% of all imports [1]. In 2022, the potato seeding area increased by 35% in Punjab, Pakistan, which represents more than 80% of national production, rising from 545,000 to 740,400 acres. Weather conditions were favorable for most of the crop's life cycle, and

growers anticipated record production [2]. Agriculture is the foundation of all civilizations, but the emphasis is on increasing production without considering the environmental impacts that have emerged due to environmental degradation [3-4]. Plant diseases are extremely important because they can significantly affect both the quality and quantity of agricultural plants. However, as this strategy may be time-consuming, costly, and inaccurate, the detection and classification of plant diseases using Deep Learning (DL) algorithms provide a rapid and accurate solution. Images of plant infection signs are used to identify plant diseases, as well as for research, education, and analysis [5-6]. In Pakistan, potato farming has become significantly important for both customers and farmers over time. In terms of production volume, it is the fourth most important crop, providing farmers with good yields and advantageous profits. With more protein and iron than other vegetables in the typical diet, potatoes are famous for their excellent nutritional value. They also provide important sources of fiber, niacin, thiamine, and other necessary elements. The Punjab province comprises over 86% of Pakistan's potato production and sowing area.

Potatoes grow in different climates, including subtropical, temperate, and tropical ones. They are classified as a "cool-weather crop", and the temperature has a significant impact on their output. Potato germination prefers a temperature of approximately 25°C, while vegetative growth does best at approximately 20°C. On the other hand, the temperature range between 16 and 24°C is ideal for tuber production, which is severely restricted though by temperatures exceeding 30°C (86°F) or below 10°C (50°F). Typically, daily temperatures between 18 and 20°C (64 and 68°F) produce the highest yields. Potatoes are very easy to grow, but since they do best in cooler climates, it is crucial to plant them at the right time. The fall crop planting season, which makes up more than 70% of the total production, starts in early October and runs until mid-November. The spring crop can be seeded from mid-December to mid-February and represents less than 10% of the overall production. On the other hand, the summer crop, which makes up more than 15% of the overall production, is planted between early April and mid-May.

Numerous microbes, including fungi, bacteria, and viruses, are considered responsible for causing plant diseases. Experts and farmers frequently diagnose these diseases by visual inspection, without the use of specialized technology. Locally produced seed potatoes satisfy more than 99% of the need for domestic potatoes consumption in Pakistan. The country currently produces about 2.02 million MT domestically each year, of which 280,000 MT is used for seed and the remaining 1.7 million MT is accessible for consumption when post-harvest losses are taken into account. With a population of about 150 million, this translates to an average annual per capita intake of 11 Kg.

TABLE I. SHARES OF SEASONAL POTATO PRODUCTION

Crop Production	Planting	Harvesting	Share
Winter	Jan-Feb	Apr-May	7.1 %
Summer	Mar-May	Aug-Oct	15-20%
Autumn	Sept-Oct	Jan-Feb	70-75%

This study aims to use DL and computer image processing to develop a quick and accurate disease detection system. DL approaches are good at classifying plant diseases [7]. An artificial infection detection method can help new gardeners and experienced plant pathologists identify plant diseases based on visual cues on plant traits. [8-9]. A CNN-based machine learning approach was used for the identification and classification of plant diseases. The dataset used consists of various plant species collected from a global data archive called "Plant Village". However, this study mainly focused on several potato plants varieties due to their importance and widespread cultivation, especially in Pakistan [10]. In [11], Artificial Intelligence (AI) was reported to offer the potential to improve crop productivity through soil and weather data analysis, helping to optimize irrigation and fertilization approaches. Furthermore, AI enables early detection of plant diseases and monitoring of plant health, facilitating prompt interventions and minimizing crop damage. Additionally, AI applications in automating farm machinery not only streamline operations but also result in cost savings and improved operational efficiency. Finally, seed potato generation allows diseases to spread quickly, as one seed potato produces about ten tubers.

In Japan, there are about 12 viruses that affect potato production [12], making disease management measures necessary for the yields to be increased. The Japanese government created a three-stage propagation system for seed potato production and distribution to encourage consistent potato production and provide disease-free and high-quality seed potatoes. The seed potato yield increased 10 times at every stage of propagation. As a result, today Japan has one of the highest potato yields per unit of land worldwide. However, healthy and disease-free seed potatoes can suffer during multiplication. Inspections utilizing various detection techniques are carried out along the propagation chain to spot and remove damaged seed potatoes and ensure their quality. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR), electron microscopy, and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) are some of the examination techniques used [13].

To design a functional and field-ready system, it is crucial to incorporate the specialized knowledge of field workers. As a result, this study included on-site consultations with experts in unusual plant identification [14]. The experts found and considered a few factors throughout these conversations, entailing:

- Plants with abnormalities can be identified in their early development.
- Compared to the early development stage, when plants are in their mid-growth stage, their neighboring plant leaves may overlap, making it harder to spot abnormal plants. Abnormal plants can be found by comparing them with nearby healthy plants.
- Leaves that show disease symptoms were taken into account during detection. A plant is considered odd if it has unusual leaves and disease symptoms.

Based on these inputs, a system that can be employed in the field was designed on the following:

- Image processing usage to identify abnormal potato plants in their early development stages. Each plant is then obtained and classified utilizing a newly created explainable deep classification model.
- Utilization of a specially designed pipeline to compare unusual potato plants with nearby plants to identify them in the mid-growth period.
- During the middle stage of growth, identifying unusual potato leaves involves engaging an existing deep learning model for leaf detection in conjunction with the proposed explainable deep classification model to categorize the identified leaves. This study developed algorithms to identify unusual potato plants, evaluated their accuracy, and examined their effectiveness under diverse field light circumstances. The DL models were developed and validated on certain datasets.

In [15], a method was proposed to recognize and classify tomato leaf diseases, using the LeNet architecture, which is a CNN variant. This architecture was used to classify images of tomato plant leaves based on the obvious symptoms of diseases and present a decision-making strategy that relies on exact judgment and scientific methodologies. Deep residual learning and transfer learning were used to train the CNN on a portion of the Plant Village dataset that contained photos of tomato plant leaves. The results showed that the proposed method was computationally economical and beat VGG models pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset in terms of accuracy and retraining time [16].

In [17], 20 agrochemicals are often uniformly administered throughout a growing season, ignoring the geographical diversity of disease infestations within a potato crop. To improve potato production, growers have augmented the uniform application of agrochemicals by 150% in the last 20 years, increasing production costs and environmental degradation. This study also discussed the benefits of effective crop management, which can be achieved by precisely applying agrochemicals. These benefits could include improved potato quality, increased tuber production, as well as financial and environmental gains [18]. The creation of intelligent sprayers that can recognize spatially variable weed and disease distribution within potato fields can allow for the targeted administration of agrochemicals only in the affected areas. Precision agriculture techniques are still in their early stages in Pakistan, although they are steadily gaining acceptance in other parts of the world. By maximizing pesticide use and supporting sustainable practices, these artificial sprayers application could revolutionize agricultural practices.

According to [19], early blight, a prevalent potato disease caused by *Alternaria Solani* Sorauer, is common throughout Pakistan. Like other plant leaf diseases, it first affects older, less productive leaves before advancing up the plant canopy and triggering leaf senescence. The first symptoms of this disease are small black or brown lesions of 1-2 mm that grow into dark-pigmented concentric rings in a favorable

environment [20]. In [21], early blight was controlled by applying fungicides indiscriminately without considering its geographical distribution. This method has an adverse effect on the environment in addition to raising production costs. An intelligent classification system that can discriminate between diseased and healthy plants and allow targeted fungicide administration is required to support economic and environmental sustainability. Implementing a precise and immediate disease detection system could accelerate the localization of affordable crop protection strategies and improve global food security. Additionally, site-specific pesticide administration can depend on accurate disease identification utilizing machine vision and DL.

In [22], a neural network-based disease detection approach was presented, subjecting a series of low-resolution photographs to principal components analysis and then introducing them into a neural network to detect plant diseases. A disease identification approach based on thresholding and picture segmentation was also proposed in [23], applying threshold levels to identify sickness in each block of sick leaf grayscale photos. In [24], a novel image segmentation technique was introduced for disease quantification, transferring color images to the I1I2I3 color space before converting them to HSV to effectively quantify diseases in various plant species. In [25], an unsupervised color-based disease-qualifying approach was used, showing greater accuracy compared to previous methods. The images were divided into many classes, and then a deterministic supervised learning technique was utilized to train each class. However, many of these technologies are not suitable for real-time application of agrochemicals because of the lengthy inference time required for image processing, despite the breakthroughs in disease identification algorithms. Fortunately, recent developments in GPU-embedded processors have resulted in a large increase in the number of applications using AI, making possible the development and implementation of novel methods and models, in particular DL techniques [26]. The sector of agriculture and crop protection may undergo a revolution due to promising DL models for faster and more effective disease identification.

GPU-based parallel computing has significantly helped the creation and deployment of CNNs across numerous applications. In [27], different CNNs were shown to have good accuracy levels on sizable datasets with a variety of image classes. CNNs have been one of the most effective DL methods for image processing in recent years. CNNs often consist of numerous layers, such as fully linked, conventional, and pooling layers. Convolution is a crucial linear action in the conventional layer since it is one of the multiple mathematical operations that are essential to CNNs [28]. According to [29], the conventional layer, which manages the significant computational load, is an essential component of a CNN. To reduce the stress on the spatial computational parameters, pooling layers are usually positioned between subsequent conventional layers. The fully connected layers have activation functions that pull the results from CNN, such as object classification. Data are kept in the form of two-dimensional grids, or arrays, in digital images. A kernel is a small unit of an array. The Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), which converts

negative pixel values to zeros to speed up the calculation and make it easier to identify targets, is one of the most widely used activation functions.

Color segmentation is applied to capture a picture of a sick leaf, and the results produce HSV characteristics. The Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is trained to distinguish between samples with and without disease. ANN classification performs 80% better than previous techniques, showing a significant gain in accuracy. On the other hand, such methods have approximately 80% accuracy, which is relatively low and causes certain detection errors. To solve this problem, in [30], a CNN method was proposed, which used leaf pictures to differentiate healthy from infected cucumbers. The CNN was used to identify two serious viral infections, Zucchini Yellow Mosaic Virus (ZYMV) and Melon Yellow Spot Virus (MYSV). The dataset utilized consisted of 800 photographs of cucumber leaves, of which 200 showed ZYMV, 300 showed MYSV, and 300 showed healthy leaves. Rotational modifications were made to expand the dataset. A CNN structure with 96 Ms, three convolutional layers, three pooling layers, and three normalization layers was suggested for the multiclassification challenge, and ReLU was employed as the activation function. This method achieved a precision score of 94.9%. Furthermore, in [31], it was shown that climate change impacts potato yield in Prince Edward Island, Canada.

As the most important thing is to detect diseases and pests in low time and cost, DL and ML are the most feasible to use. Additionally, this study highlighted the enormous influence of GPU usage on the exponential rise of AI applications. Intelligent sprayers can recognize the spatially varied distributions of weeds and diseases in potato fields. Inference times should be estimated to determine the suitability of CNNs in a smart sprayer for on-demand fungicide treatment. The addition of disease detection utilizing CNN and machine vision, as well as the investigation of the viability and practicality of integrating them into a smart sprayer, gives a sense of creativity and originality to this study. However, this study involved pre-trained inception-v3-based transfer learning weights to obtain a high-performance classification. The model was expanded by training it on the ImageNet dataset, which increases the new Inception-v3 model's learning efficiency. This method shares the learned model parameters with the new model to improve detection performance through transfer learning.

II. PROPOSED MODEL'S CNN ARCHITECTURE

Deep learning is a strong ML algorithm entailed in speech recognition, picture analysis, and image restoration. It varies from conventional ML since it employs multiple closely connected layers. This allows the output of one layer to be used as the input for the following layer. DL automatically gathers and optimizes features during the model training process, in contrast to conventional methods that necessitate feature engineering. Unsupervised, supervised, or semi-supervised learning environments can be engaged. The convolutional layer, the pooling layer, the activation function layer, and the fully connected layer make up the structure of a CNN, as shown in Figure 2. CNNs are quite effective in applications like object identification and image categorization. CNNs were

utilized for DL in the plant disease recognition project to obtain accurate plant disease recognition.

Fig. 1. The proposed method's CNN architecture.

A. Study Site and Data Collection

In Pakistan, summer typically lasts longer than the short winter. The country had completely relied on imported seed varieties until recently because there were no locally prepared potato seed variants. Four or five diseases out of a total of 18 or 19 threaten Pakistani potato crops, creating problems for the crop. Numerous diseases might be caused by using potassium and calcium fertilizers in insufficient amounts. One of the main regions in Pakistan for potato production is the one around the districts of Okara, Sahiwal, Kasur, and Pakpattan. The Sahiwal-based Potato Research Institute (PRI) has taken steps to create seven seeds. Pakistan imports seed potatoes from Germany and the Netherlands and exports potatoes to countries such as Afghanistan, Russia, the Middle East, and Germany.

Canon PowerShot SX540 and Logitech C270 HD digital cameras were used to capture pictures of healthy and diseased potato plants (Russet Burbank variety) in collaboration with a local plant pathologist to identify the visual symptoms of early blight. The observations were consistent with Kemmit's classification of blight disease early stages during the potato growing season. Photographs of the early, middle, and late phases of the disease in potato leaves were taken based on the visual symptoms observed. Early July, or around 35 Days After Planting (DAP), is when visual symptoms of early blight, such as pale, yellow-colored leaves, first appear. Around 65 DAP, the disease enters its mid-stage, which is shown by brown concentric circles on the leaves of potato plants. Finally, the disease enters its late stage around 80 DAP. These stages are shown in Figures 2-4. Since there are no effective treatments for the disease, it is essential to identify it accurately as soon as possible to minimize damage. It is important to note that because the data points in the captured frames depend on how severe the disease is, they can change in real-time. If a plant has a more severe disease than another, there may be more disease data points. Due to its development, the disease also tends to show itself in potato plants as patches.

Fig. 2. Pictures for identifying early blight disease stages on potatoes, showing the disease's early-stage leaves as being pale yellow.

Fig. 3. Mid-stage concentric brown circles in the leaves.

Fig. 4. Senescence of leaves during the disease's final stage.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The images were captured in 2023 from 9:00 a.m. to 4:00 p.m., in natural sunshine, at a height of around 140 cm. The collected photos were resized to 1280×720 pixels using a specially created Python application to speed up processing. The 1280×720-pixel resolution was chosen expressly to improve the model suitability for real-time applications. This resolution was also chosen to determine whether it would be possible to build a smart variable rate sprayer that utilizes a live camera signal by combining the proposed CNN model with hardware.

TABLE II. ACCURACY IN EACH CLASS AND OVERALL ACCURACY IN THE TRAINING AND TESTING PHASES

Plant disease	CNN training accuracy	CNN testing accuracy
Pepper bell bacterial	99.5	98.6
Pepper bell healthy	98.1	98.9
Potato early blight	97.6	98.9
Potato healthy	99.1	94.1
Potato late blight	96.3	98.9
Tomato target spot	95.7	94.1
Tomato mosaic virus	98.5	98.9
Tomato yellow leaf curl virus	97.7	99.1
Tomato bacterial spot	99.3	98.9
Tomato early blight	97.1	97.3
Tomato healthy	98.5	98.9
Tomato late blight	98.6	97.1
Tomato leaf mold	98.5	98.9
Tomato septoria leaf spot	98.1	98.2
Tomato spider mites	98.9	99.1
Overall accuracy	98.29	98.029

Photos were collected throughout the potato growing season to identify the disease stages. Various CNN models were trained using pictures of the diseases at each step, as well as pictures of the symptoms associated with each stage. Table II provides a summary of the accuracy achieved for each class throughout the test and examination phases, as well as the overall accuracy for all classes during both phases.

A. Evaluation of the Proposed Method Compared to Previous Works

1) CNNs of Two, Four, and Six Classes

During the initial early blight detection training, the validation accuracy values for each CNN ranged from 0.95 to 0.97. Compared to VGG Net and Efficient Net, GoogleNet showed a lower validation accuracy. However, as illustrated in Table III, for midstage early blight detection, all CNNs demonstrated higher validation accuracy, ranging from 0.99 to 1.00. Similarly, all CNNs' validation accuracy ranged between 0.99 and 1.00 at the final stage of early blight. The validation accuracy of the 4-class CNNs was 0.92. As shown in Table III, the validation accuracy of the joint stages (initial+mid) was somewhat worse than that of the individual stages (initial, mid, and late). The validation accuracy for the mid-to-final early blight disease stage ranged from 0.84 to 0.86. Based on the narrow accuracy range, all CNNs behaved similarly. Additionally, the initial and terminal phases of the early blight disease had a classification accuracy ranging from 0.92 to 0.94. In 4-class CNNs, the validation accuracy for the beginning and the final stages of the disease was somewhat higher than for the initial+mid and mid+last phases. On the other hand, the validation accuracy for the initial, intermediate, and terminal disease stages varied from 0.81 to 0.85 for the 6-class CNN. The 6-Class CNN suffered relatively significant training and validation losses due to the large number of identical classes, which reduced validation accuracy scores.

A Dell Latitude 5580 was used to measure the three CNNs' inference times, which varied from 121 to 145 ms. The inference time values for the CNNs in all classes fell within a similar range, showing that it had little to no impact on the different CNN classes. The VGG Net showed the fastest inference time among the three CNNs, with values ranging from 398 to 458 ms. This was mostly due to its ability to learn more parameters in a single forward pass than GoogleNet and Efficient Net. The inference speed of EfficientNet ranged from 5.95 to 6.53 fps. Compared to other CNNs, GoogleNet had the shortest inference time. The detection accuracy of GoogleNet was found to be significantly lower compared to other CNNs. On the other hand, the F1-score, recall, and precision of the VGG Net demonstrated promising results in terms of disease detection accuracy, but it is less effective for real-time applications due to its longer inference time. GoogleNet and EfficientNet offer a good balance between accuracy and inference speed, making them stronger competitors for the creation of real-time smart sprayers when both accuracy and inference speed are essential. The CNNs examined had considerably varied inference times, while GoogleNet and EfficientNet had the smallest disparities. GoogleNet and VGG Net revealed comparable inference time ranges [32]. In conclusion, the accuracy findings and statistical measurements

obtained for different CNN architectures, along with the analysis of inference time, showed that EfficientNet exhibits promise for implementation and integration into a smart sprayer for targeted fungicide treatment in potato fields. The EfficientNet is an excellent selection for further processing integration into a variable-rate smart sprayer due to its disease

detection accuracy during various stages of disease evolution, as indicated by statistical measures such as recall, precision, and F1-score, as well as its relatively quicker inference time. Through this integration, fungicide applications in potato fields will be precise and effective.

TABLE III. TRAINING AND STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE TWO, FOUR, AND SIX-CLASS CNNs FOR THE POTATO PRODUCTION SYSTEM IN CLASSIFYING THE EARLY BLIGHT DISEASE STAGES

Class	Model	Growth Stage	1 Val Acc	2 Val Loss	3 Tr Loss	Precision	Recall
Two-class CNNs	GoogleNet	Beginning	0.96	0.33	0.01	0.8	0.91
		Middle	1.00	0.03	0.01	0.92	0.94
		Final	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.83	0.87
	VGGNet	Beginning	0.96	0.61	0.00	0.88	0.87
		Middle	0.99	0.04	0.01	0.97	0.95
		Final	0.99	0.06	0.00	0.88	0.9
	EfficientNet	Beginning	0.96	0.08	0.02	0.90	0.90
		Middle	0.98	0.03	0.10	0.98	0.89
		Final	0.99	0.02	0.10	0.90	0.90
Four-class CNNs	GoogleNet	Beginning + Middle	0.93	0.29	0.10	0.90	0.86
		Middle + Final	0.90	0.59	0.29	0.87	0.89
		Beginning + Final	0.93	0.10	0.10	0.95	0.95
	VGGNet	Beginning + Middle	0.92	0.27	0.01	0.84	0.85
		Middle + Final	0.86	0.13	0.07	0.79	0.78
		Beginning + Final	0.93	0.25	0.12	0.88	0.88
	EfficientNet	Beginning + Middle	0.92	0.01	0.01	0.88	0.88
		Middle + Final	0.84	0.79	0.30	0.85	0.85
		Beginning + Final	0.89	0.09	0.10	0.99	0.98
Six-class CNNs	GoogleNet	Beginning + Middle + Final	0.81	0.21	0.08	0.74	0.74
	VGGNet	Beginning + Middle + Final	0.82	0.32	0.12	0.73	0.72
	EfficientNet	Beginning + Middle + Final	0.85	0.12	0.02	0.74	0.75

1 Val acc = validation accuracy; 2 Val Loss = validation loss; 3 Tr loss = training loss.

2) CNN and Deep Learning Frameworks

CNNs may now be operated more easily due to advances made in DL and machine vision. Multiple frameworks have been developed to improve computational efficiency for a variety of applications, including Caffe, Torch, Theano, and others. Large and complicated computational models may be built using DL frameworks, while they also make it easier to calculate gradient losses, which reduces the discrepancy between projected and real-world data. Given the intensive processing requirements of CNNs, the use of a GPU-enabled workstation speeds up images training and validation utilizing DL frameworks. Some frameworks integrate networking between the CPU, GPU, and memory with DL libraries. This study chose the PyTorch framework for all CNN-related tasks, including training, validation, and testing, due to its accessibility to resources, GPU support, and simplicity [33-34]. This research examined three CNNs, VGGNet, EfficientNet, and GoogleNet, for early blight disease identification at different stages, based on their suitability for commercial applications, real-time performance, and accuracy. Among these models, GoogleNet was considered the one with the most precise predictions, as it successfully identified plant diseases and parts in [35-36]. The VGG Net design employs three convolutional filters to increase accuracy and eliminate overfitting issues [37]. This architecture provides a few choices with varying layer levels, including Vgg-11, Vgg-13, and Vgg-16. This study evaluated the efficiency of the most recent version, VGGNet-16, in classifying diseases at various stages. EfficientNet was created using a methodical approach to

network depth, breadth, and resolution [38]. Based on the compound scaling technique, EfficientNet is said to be a light and accurate model. This study used the lightweight EfficientNet model B0, which is renowned for its accurate performance according to picture results.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Agriculture plays a vital role in the development of any country economy [39]. This study investigated several dataset combinations with various CNNs to identify and categorize early blight disease in potato production. All CNNs examined demonstrated the ability to distinguish between damaged and healthy plants with varied degrees of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The outcomes showed that, at different stages of disease identification, EfficientNet and VGGNet both outperformed GoogleNet. In contrast to EfficientNet and VGGNet, GoogleNet had the shortest inference time. Applying fungicides to sick parts of potato crops with a machine vision and DL-based sprayer has a great potential to reduce agrochemicals in agricultural fields. It is interesting to investigate the integration of these models in Variable Rate Sprayers (VRS) to manage and monitor potato crops in real-time. However, it is important to anticipate potential challenges, such as conflicting detection signals encountered by the sprayer nozzle due to various factors, such as multiple diseases, diverse potato plant species, and different ground surface covers. This paper focused on early blight, the predominant potato disease in Pattoki, Punjab, Pakistan. Future research involves broadening this study to encompass a broader

spectrum of diseases, diverse potato varieties, and alternative farming approaches.

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Critical Risk Factors influencing Time Schedule of Residential Projects in Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Delays in residential construction projects are common issues in both developing and developed countries. This research aims to identify the key reasons behind these delays in Pakistan. When the projects run behind schedule, this can lead to problems such as exceeding the budget, reduced productivity at the construction site, and potentially lower quality work. The study involved a detailed survey using questionnaires that were addressed to industry professionals. Their responses were used to rank the critical factors causing delays. The most significant factors were found to be fluctuating material prices, financial challenges for contractors, underestimating project duration, poor site management, inexperienced contractors, ineffective project management, communication gaps among project stakeholders, shortage of skilled workers, changes in project design, unqualified contractors, and inadequate project planning. Identifying these critical factors through the Relative Importance Index (RII) method can help in addressing and preventing delays in Pakistan's construction projects, ensuring timely completion and better project outcomes in the future.

Keywords-time overrun; construction delays; critical factors; Pakistan; survey

I. INTRODUCTION

Time overrun is one of the most critical issues in the construction industry [1]. Construction time overrun is defined as a change between the project's actual contract period at the time of the tender and its final contract period when the project is completed. Time overrun can lead to problems in various aspects, such as budget overruns, low productivity, etc., which can result in poor-quality performance, and dissatisfaction among project stakeholders [2]. In [3], it is reported that in Pakistan, out of 65 projects, only 2 were completed on time, while the remaining 63 projects were delayed for various reasons [3]. In Saudi Arabia, approximately 70% of residential construction projects have experienced schedule overruns [4]. Delays are one of the most serious problems associated with construction projects, as they can lead to the initial estimated time and cost being exceeded. The only way to mitigate these delays is through proper identification and study of their causes [5]. The majority of projects in Pakistan have been completed after the defined time, while very little research has been conducted to identify the critical factors contributing to time

overruns in building projects in Pakistan [6]. Many large residential projects are delayed due to numerous factors that play a critical role in controlling project timelines. Delays tend to occur during the execution phase, which is considered the most crucial stage in the construction life cycle, with various factors contributing to project delays. According to the Lahore Development Authority (LDA), approximately 50% of residential projects in Lahore city are halted due to poor project management and estimation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Overview of Construction Industry

The construction industry involves various disciplines that collaborate with each other to meet the requirements of construction projects. This collaboration includes roles like architectural engineering design, construction and procurement engineering, as well as risk management, project management, and ensuring the sustainability of the project, among others. Construction can be categorized into different forms, including industry-specific, commercial buildings, and in-situ residential

construction projects [7]. In Pakistan, there is a significant ongoing construction activity, especially in residential construction projects, which are gaining popularity due to the increasing population in various parts of the cities. The construction field is the second-largest sector in Pakistan, contributing approximately 33% of the total GDP, making it the second-highest contributor after the agriculture sector. The construction industry is considered one of the most important and sustainable businesses, with consistent growth in the past decade. However, there are several risks associated with this domain, including geopolitical factors, resource availability, technology considerations, and sometimes economic impacts.

B. Overview of Pakistan's Construction Industry

The estimated market size of Pakistan's construction industry was \$17.4 billion in 2022. According to projections for the 2024-2027 period, research indicates that there will be an increase of 5% to 10%, respectively. This growth will be supported by investments in various sectors, including transportation, electricity, housing schemes, telecommunications, and a focus on infrastructural projects. The key sectors within Pakistan's construction industry are further divided into subgroups, as per the Pakistan's Construction Association. These subgroups include industrial, energy and utility, residential, and infrastructure construction.

1) Industrial Construction

This sector is expected to experience significant growth in the near future, contributing to the economy of Pakistan. According to the vision for 2030, there are plans for extensive industrial construction throughout the entire region of Pakistan.

2) Energy and Utilities Construction

The energy and utilities sector is also anticipated to expand in the foreseeable future due to the increasing population in the country. This growth is necessary to meet the rising demands for energy and utilities in Pakistan.

3) Residential Construction

Residential construction is indeed one of the fastest-growing construction sectors in Pakistan. This growth is driven by the increasing population, which relies on residential areas for their accommodation needs. The construction of new residential units is essential to accommodate the expanding population in the future.

4) Infrastructure Construction

Infrastructure construction is also expected to increase in the future, particularly through public-private partnerships. This approach is aimed at stabilizing the country's economy and deriving more benefits from such construction methods. It signifies a collaborative effort to enhance and develop the infrastructure, which is essential for economic growth and overall prosperity.

C. Reasons of Delays in Construction Industry

1) Inexcusable Delays

These delays are attributable to situations where the contractor bears full responsibility for extending the project's duration. In these cases, the contractor is obligated to cover any

damages resulting from their own actions. For example, this could occur due to a lack of proper equipment necessary for the job, a shortage of essential materials, or inadequate planning and allocation of labor during working hours.

2) Excusable Delays

These delays are primarily caused by unforeseeable events that are beyond the contractor's control. In such cases, the contractor usually receives some leniency or understanding from the client. Examples of these events include incidents like fires at the site from unknown sources, natural disasters such as floods or earthquakes, and severe weather conditions.

D. Past Research Studies

Past researchers have conducted a research on time overrun factors in different kinds of construction projects in order to find out the most critical factors and the most important causes of the time overrun in the residential construction projects. Authors in [8] conducted a detailed survey on field engineers and identified the main causes of the time overrun in construction projects. The main identified causes were delay in payments, shortage of materials, changes and amendments in the selected materials, poor site management, and poor financial status of client. Authors in [9] identified 33 common factors which cause time overrun and divided them further into 8 subgroups. The research was conducted using the Relative Importance Index (RII) and the 5 identified main important factors for time overrun were poor site supervision, delays in decision making from client and contractor, changes in the design during the execution phase, the poor site investigation, and poor site management from the execution staff. Authors in [10] reported as the most critical causes in delays financial issues faced by contractors, inexperienced contractor selection for the project, severe weather conditions, lack of skilled workers at site, errors in time estimation of the project, and mistakes in design. Authors in [11] identified major risk factors in terms of external, internal and force majeure in the aviation construction projects which caused delays and time overruns during the construction phase. Authors in [12] figured out 29 direct and 32 indirect dispute causes, out of which direct dispute caused delays due to unrealistic contract duration, poor quality of work, lack of skilled labor, lack in payments from the client, indirect disputes, poor project planning and scheduling by the workers and contractor, poor estimation of the project, and contractor's lack of experience. Authors in [13] identified the most critical factors which cause time overruns in the construction projects in Vietnam using the quantitative approach. From the contractor's side, the main cause was the poor monitoring of the project and poor project management whereas from the owners side, financial problems caused delays in the construction activities. This research was evaluated through a question survey which was sent to professionals.

Table I summarizes the results of the recent research on the topic of time overruns and delays.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of the current research is to assess the factors leading to time overruns and delays in residential

construction projects in Pakistan. To achieve this, the following steps were taken: initially, the key factors were categorized, and the RII statistical technique was employed to evaluate them based on the responses collected from experienced professionals. The main purpose for selecting this technique was to get the values of each factor and rank them accordingly. Subsequently, a critical analysis was conducted to rank these factors, identifying the most critical ones. The primary goal of using this technique was to rank the factors through a statistical analysis of the data gathered from feedback and responses.

TABLE I. CRITICAL FACTOR CAUSING TIME OVERRUN IDENTIFIED BY RECENT RESEARCH

Ref.	Country	Findings
[14]	Jordan	The primary causes of delays in public construction projects are often associated with design changes, severe weather conditions, late material deliveries, variations in quantities due to inaccurate estimations, and the poor economic condition of the country.
[15]	Thailand	Material shortages, inadequate project planning, changes in project scope by clients and owners, and poor management by the execution team and contractor.
[16]	Ghana	Poor contract management, delays in material procurement, poor project performance by the project team, and increases in material prices.
[17]	Saudi Arabia	The author identified 56 main causes of delays in construction, with some of the most significant factors being delays in the approval and preparation of shop drawings, design changes during execution, poor relationships between contractors and subcontractors, and slow decision-making processes.
[18]	Nigeria	Delays caused by clients often include variations in project scope, decision-making issues, and cash flow problems. Delays attributed to the contractor may arise from poor project planning and scheduling, ineffective site management and execution, and delayed delivery of materials.

IV. DATA COLLECTION AND DATA ANALYSIS

In the initial phase, a questionnaire survey was designed and distributed to 89 professionals, including consultants, clients, and contractors, who were actively engaged in residential construction projects. The purpose of this survey was to gather data based on their personal responses. Once the data were collected through this comprehensive survey, they were analyzed using the RII to identify the most and the least critical factors that could impact the timely completion of residential projects. The outcomes of the distributed survey are presented in Table II and Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Percentage of responses from clients, contractors, and consultants.

TABLE II. EXPERIENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage
More than 15 years	23	25.8
Less than 15 years	66	74.2
Total Respondents	89	100

The factors were ranked after a thorough analysis using the RII, where a higher RII value corresponded to a higher rank. A higher ranking number indicates that the factor has a more significant impact on causing time schedule overruns and delays in the project timelines. The formula for the RII is:

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{(A \times N)} \tag{1}$$

The final results are exhibited in Table IV, and are further analyzed below.

TABLE III. RANKING OF CRITICAL FACTORS CAUSING TIME OVERRUN

Factors	RII	Rank
Fluctuation in material prices	0.913	1
Financial difficulties faced by contractor	0.904	2
Underestimation of project duration	0.831	3
Poor site management	0.819	4
Lack of experience of the selected contractor	0.790	5
Poor project management	0.784	6
Lack of communication among project parties	0.761	7
Shortage of skilled workers	0.755	8
Changes in design	0.740	9
Incompetent contractor	0.732	10
Poor project planning and management	0.729	11

A. Fluctuation in Material Prices

Fluctuation in prices is one of the major causes of the delays in the residential construction projects, with a RII value of 0.913. The timeline of the project is based on the availability of the materials and if the prices of the material increase, the project will get affected, while this can lead to work stoppage.

B. Financial Difficulties Faced by the Contractor

Financial issues faced by contractor have a RII value of 0.904. Usually, contractors undergo finance related issues due to which they are unable to make the payments to the sub-contractor and as a result project suffers delays [20].

C. Underestimation of Project Duration

Underestimation of project duration or errors in time estimation can cause problems in the project to be finished on time, so there must be a properly defined timeline for the project. The RII value for this factor is 0.831.

D. Poor Site Management

Poor site management causes delays in the project schedule because if the construction activities are not overlooked properly, there might be some problems due to which the project deadlines get extended. The value for RII is 0.784.

E. Lack of Experience of the Selected Contractor

Sometimes clients select contractors with not enough experience, usually for financial reasons, so the schedule of the project gets eventually disturbed. This factor has a RII value of 0.790.

F. Poor Project Management

Due to poor project management, the projects does not get completed on time. The RII value for this factor is 0.784.

G. Lack of Communication among Project Parties

Most of the time, lack of sufficient communication among project stakeholders causes a lot of problems during project life-cycle and timelines get affected. Different tools and techniques can be used for effective communication among project parties. The RII value of this factor is 0.761.

H. Shortage of Skilled Labor

Most of the time, the project team do not get enough labor to complete the project activities on time and due to this the project gets delayed and the overall objectives of the projects are not achievable. The obtained RII value was 0.755.

I. Changes in Design

Due to the lack of communication between the design department and the contractor, changes in design can cause problems in the time schedule. This factor has an RII value of 0.740. Changes in design in any stage of the project can make things very complex for all project stakeholders.

J. Incompetent Contractor

Incompetent contractors may not complete the project on time. Selection of a competent contractor is the responsibility of the client and the consultant. The RII value of this factor is 0.729.

K. Poor Project Planning and Management

Due to poor project planning and management of the execution work, the project team does not have enough time and capabilities to finish the project on time. This factor scored the lowest RII value of 0.729.

V. CONCLUSION

The main aim of this research was to find out the most critical factors which impact the residential construction projects in Pakistan. After the statistical analysis, we figured out the 11 most critical factors, which were, in descending order of importance, fluctuation in the prices of the material, financial difficulties faced by the contractor during the project life, underestimation of the project duration, inexperienced contractors, poor project management, lack of communication among project parties, shortage of site workers, changes in design, incompetent contractors, and poor project planning and management.

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Fracture Analysis of a Cycloidal Gearbox as a Yaw Drive on a Wind Turbine

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ABSTRACT

Fast growth of renewable energies has required addressing challenges such as generating the largest energy production possible throughout the equipment's lifespan and between its preventive and corrective maintenance intervals. Actions such as preventive maintenance, and improvement of the main components, mainly when it comes to reliability and predictability are of extreme importance to reach maximum generation. Due to the importance of the yaw drives for wind turbines, this paper aims to evaluate a failure that occurred on a cycloidal gearbox used in a drive of this kind. For the evaluation of the yaw drive, all the components were analyzed to determine the incurred fracture mechanism. Such analysis was performed by mapping all components, conducting a hardness test to check the components' mechanical properties, analysis of the fractured surfaces of the cycloidal disc, and numerical simulation (linear elastic) via the Finite Element Method (FEM) to check the stress distribution on the fractured part (cycloidal disc) under load, and theoretical calculation of the cycloidal disc lifespan. In addition, the stress distribution by FEM was compared with the broken regions of the physical part. To sum up, after all the evaluations, it is possible to claim the results demonstrate there was a premature fracture of the cycloidal disc that occurred due to the phenomenon of high cycle fatigue.

Keywords-fracture analysis; yaw drive; numerical simulation; Finite Element Method (FEM)

I. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy is the spinal column of any energy source shifting to fulfill a net zero emission [1]. Consequently, there are many machines and pieces of equipment that aim to utilize renewable sources like harvesting air flow or transforming sun energy into electricity, and for this purpose, continuous efforts have been made to combine both technologies [2, 3]. Particularly about windmill projects [4-6], which is the topic covered in this paper, the highest energy efficiency is obtained when the windmill harvests the maximum amount of energy from different currents of airflow throughout the maximum number of days possible. To reach the objective of maximum power from a machine, it must perform at its maximum resource and its components must have a predictable life. For that, preventive maintenance and operation variable monitoring are instrumental [7, 8]. This challenge ends up motivating scientists and engineers to strive to raise the performance and promote the improvement of these components. In this context, important patents have been registered worldwide [4, 9] along with many published scientific papers that have helped to improve the machine components' performance [10, 11]. Particularly about yaw drives, there are multiple brands and models in the market, the

most common designs have multiple stage planetary stages that generate low speed and torque according to the needs [12]. However, there is another type, called cycloidal planetary transmissions, which delivers the advantage over the classic transmissions due to its inverter or involute planetary gears. These drives are smaller, silent, work smoothly, are efficient, and deliver a high gear value, which could be translated as higher power density [13-15].

The novelty of this paper resides in presenting a fracture of cycloidal yaw drives, which is not found in the literature. This paper aims to provide an analysis of the components of the yaw gearbox like bearings, crankshafts, pinion, housings, gears, cycloidal disc, etc., providing a diagnosis of the gearboxes and determining the root cause for equipment failure. The yaw drive evaluated was a cycloidal gearbox with a spur gear stage and a second cycloidal stage [16, 17] driven by four crankshafts.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

For disassembling the yaw gearbox, regular wrenches and a hydraulic press were utilized to remove the output gear from the pinion shaft. In addition, mapping and visual inspection of all the parts were conducted along with identification per

disassembly phase/stage. The fractured surfaces passed through visual analysis by comparing the fractured surfaces with the literature [24-25]. Moreover, hardness test of the parts was performed by using a portable hardness tester, Accusize Tool Hardness Tester NIST traceable, and a 3D model was produced in Autodesk F-360 [18] along with a Finite Element Method (FEM) final analysis [19-30]. With those data, it was possible to predict the lifespan of the cycloidal disc as [21-24].

$$\sigma_a = \frac{\Delta \epsilon_e}{2} \cdot E = \sigma'_f \cdot (2N)^b$$

$$\therefore \frac{\Delta \epsilon_e}{2} \cdot E = 2N = \left(\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma'_f} \right)^{\frac{1}{b}} \quad (1)$$

where σ_a is the alternating stress amplitude, $\Delta \epsilon_e/2$ the elastic strain amplitude under load (mm), E is Young's Module (210,000 MPa), σ'_f is the fatigue strength coefficient, $2N$ is the number of reversals to failure, and b is the fatigue strength exponent.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The gearbox was received on a pallet with transversal wood bars to protect it against impacts (Figure 1). A total of 4 gearboxes were delivered, but only one of them passed through analysis. The electrical motor was not included in the pallet. From the outside, there is no damage in the housing, oil leakage, plugs missing, or screws. Furthermore, the output pinion does not contain corrosion or damage to the gear teeth.

Fig. 1. Yaw gearboxes as received.

Figure 2 illustrates the disassembled output gear, the main shaft, and its spline. It can be seen that although the output gear is not damaged, it has corrosion on the internal spline. The body of the main shaft shows profound dents and small scratches certainly produced during the internal collision of pieces of metal. As a common knowledge in the cycloidal gearbox, the cycloidal discs are those that transfer the highest torque, therefore, the ones more likely to have high stresses. Another checking point was the condition of the spur gears in the first stage (Figure 3). They are in good condition, with no marks, high wearing, or deep corrosion identified.

Fig. 2. Output gear, shaft spline with its upper base.

Fig. 3. Stage 1 Spur gears and teeth condition.

The disassembling process continued, and the second stage was reached, where a major collapse occurred. To better map the failure, the cycloidal disc legs were labeled with letters from A to H to have a better understanding of the fracture mechanism of each fractured location, and further on to analyze them as pieces of the whole part (Figure 4).

Figure 5 shows that legs A and B had, as indicated by arrows, two crack nucleation spots at leg A were verified as well as a crack starting on the casting at Leg B at the right downside of the figure. As a highlight, between legs, A and B, the bearing bores are located. Figure 6 on the left (Leg C) shows a final fracture on the cross-section, which differs from the right side (Leg D) where a crack initiated on the opposite side of the bearing bore (corner) but moved towards it and another at the bearing bore surface.

Fig. 4. Overview of the cycloidal disc.

Fig. 5. Leg A (left) and Leg B (right) – arrows indicate crack nucleation.

Fig. 6. Leg C (left) and D (right) – arrows indicate crack nucleation spots.

Fig. 7. Leg E (left) and F (right).

On the left side of Figure 7 (Leg E) a double layer of material is verified which suggests an underlayer, where a crack began, and an abrupt detachment happened before the final failure. On the right, (Leg F) an intense fretting after the final fracture is suggested [29]. The arrow in the left of Figure 8 (Leg G) reveals a crack initiating at the corner of the cross-section at the casting side of the part, Figure 8 (right – Leg H) shows at least two points of crack nucleation with a perceptible distance between the beach marks, probably because of due to a more intense strain cycling close to the part collapse [25].

Fig. 8. Leg G (left) and H (right)- arrows indicate cracks in nucleation spots.

Fig. 9. Broken part of the cycloidal disc showing multiple cracks – arrows on both sides indicate the regions verified in Figure 11, the center arrow pointing to G shows multiple cracks.

The central arrow in Figure 9 reveals multiple cracks on the Leg G surface and large deformations, which indicate a high level of stress in multiple directions, suggesting torsional loading as well as radial and axial ones, most likely due to the high instability throughout the fracture process. Figure 10 shows the outer fracture of the cycloidal disc close to Legs G and H, as indicated in Figure 9 by arrows on both sides. Leg G on the left side, shows the crack initiating on the external side of the bearing bore (casting), while in Leg H the crack started at the external diameter of the cycloidal disc.

The crankshafts were analyzed in terms of major deformations. All shafts show deep plastic deformation on the bearing region. Those deformations are due to high pressure by the bearing rolls on the shaft surface during failure (Figure 11). The bearings were also evaluated and visually checked for dents, marks, or corrosion. Although they are in good condition, the regular procedure for every service is to replace them due to clearance uncertainty (Figure 12).

Fig. 10. Leg G (left) and Leg H (right) – arrows show the crack nucleation spots.

Fig. 11. Crankshaft.

Fig. 12. Bearing that drives the cycloidal disc.

The output flange in Figure 13 shows a solid part with no deformations, only a few expected scratches during operation and disassembling.

Fig. 13. Output flange.

Another characteristic evaluated during the failure analysis was the part's hardness, which aimed to check any inconsistency with regular gearbox designs. Table I illustrates the values measured on each part. The harnesses are according to the expected values utilized in designing gearboxes, except the output flange's lower value, even though these parts did not contribute to the failure. After the hardness measurement, 3D modeling was produced, and just after that Finite Element Method (FEM) calculation was executed (Figure 14) to verify whether the highest stress spots were the ones where the cracks initiated. The 3D modeling took into consideration the

dimensions of the physical part (cycloidal disc). The mesh applied was a tetrahedral element (parabolic functions), with maximum turn angle on curves of 10 degrees, maximum adjacent mesh size ratio of 1.5, maximum aspect ratio of 10, and minimum element size of 20% of the average size. The center bore had a frictionless constraint on it, the pins on the external side of the cycloidal disc were fixed for all directions (u_x , u_y , and u_z) and the load was applied on every bearing bore where the crankshaft drives the cycloidal discs, exactly as the gearbox works. For the numerical FEM simulation, a nominal torque of 12,250 Nm was applied, which was based on the model of the gearbox [18].

TABLE I. HARDNESS OF EACH COMPONENT

Part	Description	Measured
1	Spur gear	55 HRC
2	Output flange	220 HB
3	Crankshaft	59 HRC
4	Cycloidal disc – close to the external diameter	60 HRC
5	Cycloidal disc – close to the centered bore	55 HRC

Fig. 14. 3D modeling and mesh applied on the cycloidal disc.

Figure 15 presents the regions with the higher stresses located at the external radius in the groove close to the disc external diameter (170.2 MPa) and regions on the same profile but now on the flat surface that neighbors the bearing bore (75.1 MPa). Those regions on the cycloidal disc coincide with the cracks-initiated regions at the part. However, the stress level is expressively low when compared to the hardened material's mechanical strength [25].

Fig. 15. Output results from the FEM calculations.

Based on the FEM calculations and the number of cycles to fracture under normal conditions for this application, the fatigue is considered high-cycle fatigue, which means it is characterized as having a low-strain regime where the nominal strain is linear elastic. Therefore, as mentioned above, the number of cycles to fatigue was determined by (1). Since the chemical composition or the metallurgical condition of the parts were not determined, and only their hardness was measured, there was a need to assume materials with similar hardnesses, particularly for the disc. The values assumed for the calculation were from two similar materials, SAE 1045 quenched and tempered (Q&T) to 180°C, and the material 35CrMo quenched and tempered (Q&T) to 400°C, both materials usually applied as materials for gearbox parts. Table II shows the expected high cycle fatigue of similar materials used as references.

TABLE II. MATERIALS USED TO CALCULATE THE HIGH-CYCLE LIFETIME

Material	Q&T	σ_f'	b	2N
SAE 1045 [25]	180 °C	2,261	-0.089	4.24×10^{12}
35CrMo [29]	400 °C	2,030	-0.081	1.98×10^{13}

The obtained values couldn't be reached during the whole yaw drive lifespan, which suggests abnormalities on the cycloidal disc during operation. As a reference, the material 35CrMo might have a stress amplitude of 550 MPa for an infinite fatigue life ($>10^6$ cycles) – based on the S-N curve – which is much higher than the 170.2 MPa calculated via FEM.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Although there was a high level of damage in the cycloidal gearbox, particularly on the cycloidal disc, the failure did not occur due to high impacts or intense vibrations during operation. A progressive failure occurred, evidenced by the nucleation of multiple cracks, their propagation, and ending up to the final failure of the cycloidal disc. Furthermore, despite the Finite Element Method showing some spots as candidates to nucleate cracks under cyclical loading, the additional regions where multiple cracks started even under low-stress levels suggest that the parts experienced many loads as torque and forces on orthogonal axes. The failure is considered abnormal and unexpected because the theoretical number of cycles, under normal conditions of operation, is expressively larger than any yaw drive operation, which means the cycloidal disc is the last part to fail, after roller bearings, crankshafts, etc.

To sum up, it is possible to conclude that premature failure occurred due to the phenomena of high-cycle fatigue, which disregard the possibilities of either high impacts or vibrations during operation. The abnormalities' most likely root causes might be related to problems with the casting, heat treatment, or retained austenite in the microstructure, temper, or hydrogen embrittlement. To reach a profound evaluation and solid conclusion, the use of an SEM microscope is necessary, which will be covered in a following paper.

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A Comparative Study of the Oxidation Behavior of Hot-Rolled Steel established from Medium and Thin Slabs oxidized in 20% H₂O-N₂ at 600-900°C

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the oxidation behavior of oxide scale on hot-rolled steel from a Thailand steel industry. Hot-rolled steel established from the medium and thin slabs was studied. The oxidation behavior was conducted in a horizontal furnace with 20% H₂O-N₂ to simulate steel oxidation during the hot rolling line. The scale was formed at a temperature range of 600-900°C for 30, 60, and 90 min. The scale morphology can be seen via Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM-EDS). The oxide phase was investigated via X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). The results show that iron oxides such as hematite (Fe₂O₃) and magnetite (Fe₃O₄) were produced on the studied steel. The oxidation behavior of the studied steel was followed by a parabolic law. The mass gain increased with increasing temperatures. The steel established from a medium slab exhibited a lower oxidation rate than the steel established from a thin slab. The reason for this could be the high amount of oxide containing silicon at the steel-scale interface, which promoted the oxidation resistance of the steel established from the medium slab. The influence of different slab types and its alloying elements was studied to comprehend the oxidation behavior. As a result, the alloying element in the hot-rolled steel was controlled in the design process.

Keywords-oxidation; water vapor; hot-rolled steel; medium slab; thin slab

I. INTRODUCTION

In Thailand, recycling steel or producing it in Electric Arc Furnaces (EAFs) rather than Blast Furnaces (BFs) are the primary methods of manufacturing steel. Steel is primarily manufactured using scraps as basic materials. The thickness of the slab produced by the furnaces could be used to classify them, i.e. the conventional slab manufactured by the BF process typically has a thickness of about 200 mm. In the EAF process, the scraps can make a medium slab, when the thickness is ca. 80 to 100 mm or a thin slab when the thickness is ca. 50 mm [1, 2]. Metallic iron is the majority constituent of the slab produced via the EAF process. Si, Cu, and Sn as contaminants in scraps are challenging to oxidize and remove through the steelmaking process. Furthermore, Si may be present in steel within a range of 0.03 to 0.25 wt.% as a deoxidizer element during the steelmaking process, while the

acceptable range for copper content is between 0.12 and 0.20 wt.% [1]. Oxide scale always accumulates on the hot-rolled steel surface during the rolling process [3-5]. Hematite (Fe₂O₃), magnetite (Fe₃O₄), and wustite (FeO) are the major layers found in the oxide scales that form on the steel surface [3-8]. The morphologies of the oxide scales differ according to the alloying elements [9-14] and oxidizing atmosphere [15-19]. Stainless steel or alloy steel models have been used in many studies, but there are a limited number of studies regarding hot-rolled steel [20-25]. There are some studies on the effect of silicon alloys on oxide formation [26-30]. Some research has been conducted on the effects of the presence of water vapors on the oxidation behavior of low-carbon steel [31-33]. Studying the oxidation behavior of hot-rolled steel established from medium and thin slabs is the purpose of the current paper. In particular, Si plays an important role in alloying and oxidation behavior.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Hot-rolled low-carbon steel with silicon concentrations of 0.173 and 0.242 wt.% is the focus of this study. The specimen is cut from steel strips made from slabs that were produced using the electric arc furnace process, manufactured by the G Steel Public Company Limited. The specimen contained a higher Si content steel established from a medium slab with a final thickness of 2.2 mm after hot rolling and a lower Si content steel established from a thin slab with a final thickness of 2.4 mm after hot rolling. These steels had comparable finishing and coiling temperatures of 880 °C and 580 °C, respectively. Table I lists the chemical compositions of the studied steels.

TABLE I. CHEMICAL COMPOSITIONS (WT.%) OF THE STUDIED HOT-ROLLED STEELS

Steel established from	C	Si	Cu	Mn	P	S	Fe
Medium slab	0.067	0.242	0.199	0.387	0.007	0.008	Bal.
Thin slab	0.057	0.173	0.195	0.376	0.020	0.005	Bal.

SEM (Quanta 450) observations of the scale morphology and cross-section were conducted to study the oxide scales. EDS (X-Max) is an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy technique that uses element analysis. Using the XRD D8 Advance technique, the Cu K α line (0.15406 nm) with 0.02 degrees/step step size and 0.5 s/step step time is used to identify the phases that occur following the oxidation. The prepared hot-rolled steel has dimensions of 10 mm width, 10 mm length, and 2 mm thickness. Before being exposed to oxidation in the horizontal furnace, the sample was polished to eliminate the oxide scale as received from the hot rolling process. The oxide scale on the sample was grounded to a 1200 grid using SiC papers. Afterward, it was given a final cleaning with alcohol in an ultrasonic machine, dried in air, and then taken instantly to the furnace. The oxidation atmosphere within the furnace consisted of 20% water vapor and 80% nitrogen, for 30, 60, and 90 min at a flow rate of 1.2 L/min at temperatures between 600 and 900°C. In this atmosphere, the temperature control of the heating machine for the water-containing vessel was set at 60°C with a 20°C/min of heating rate applied to the furnace. Once the furnace reached the desired temperature, the sample and water vapor were delivered into it. After the variable time oxidation, nitrogen was fed into the furnace until it has cooled to room temperature. Finally, mass gain was measured by an electronic microbalance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The steel which mainly contained iron was oxidized to form three oxide scales, Fe₂O₃, Fe₃O₄, and FeO. Initially, the oxidation rate was controlled by the oxygen diffusion to the surface reaction. The process rate in this instance remained constant. Through this process, a non-protective porous scale could be formed. The oxidation kinetics corresponds to the linear law:

$$\frac{\Delta m}{A} = k_l \cdot t \quad (1)$$

where Δm is the mass gain (g), A is the surface area (cm²), k_l is the linear rate constant (g.cm⁻².s⁻¹), and t as the oxidation time (s).

Finally, the diffusion of iron through the scale controls the oxidation rate. Normally, the steel surface produces a protective non-porous scale. The oxidation rate followed the parabolic law:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta m}{A}\right)^2 = k_p \cdot t \quad (2)$$

where Δm is the mass gain (g), A is the surface area (cm²), k_p is the parabolic rate constant (g.cm⁻².s⁻¹), and t is the oxidation time (s).

The process of metal oxidation involved an inward diffusion of electrons through the scale layer, which was accompanied by the transfer of iron cations from the metal toward the oxide-gas interface. Figure 1 shows an illustrated cross-sectional view of a forming oxide scale.

Fig. 1. Ion and electron transport on a growing oxide scale.

XRD was applied to the hot-rolled steel. Peaks of hematite and magnetite were clearly detected, as shown in Figure 2. The morphology of the oxide scale on both specimens under simulated oxidation is shown in Figure 3. An oxide layer was formed when steel was oxidized in 20%H₂O-N₂ at 900°C for 90 min. The interfacial layer exhibits Fe, O, and C peaks as well as a Si peak when using Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS). The scale on steel established from a medium slab was thinner than that established from a thin slab, possibly due to the higher oxide containing Si or fayalite, present at the scale-steel interface which revealed a decreased scaling rate of the former steel.

The oxygen generated from water vapor dissociation oxidizes the iron. The oxidation of iron and oxygen should be followed in the high oxygen activity condition. The classic three-layered oxide scale should follow this route:

From thermodynamic calculations, the dissociation of 20% water vapor was finally accomplished. The partial pressure of the oxygen in the reactor was much higher than its partial pressure in equilibrium when forming the oxides. In the gas

phase, the partial pressure of oxygen was 1.90×10^{-5} atm at 900 °C, which was sufficiently higher than the oxygen partial pressure in equilibrium with wustite/magnetite/hematite formations, which was 2.51×10^{-17} atm, 1.80×10^{-15} atm, and 1.10×10^{-8} atm respectively. It can be confirmed that the iron oxides detected in this work can be thermodynamically formed under the studied conditions. Hydrogen atoms in the form of hydrogen gas (H_2) can be dissolved in the oxide. In a static mode, the hydrogen dissolved in the oxide was formed by assuming that the partial pressures of the gases in the reactor were constant. The thermodynamic information of the oxidation reaction was calculated using the data compiled from [34, 35] and the result is shown in Table II.

TABLE II. THERMODYNAMIC INFORMATION ON OXIDATION REACTIONS

Reaction	$G_{900^\circ\text{C}} \text{ (J)}$	P_{H_2O}/P_{H_2}	$P_{O_2} \text{ (atm)}$
$H_2O \rightarrow H_2 + 1/2O_2$	181,720	523,560	1.90×10^{-5}
$2Fe_3O_4 + H_2O \rightarrow 3Fe_2O_3 + H_2$	92,394	13,018	1.10×10^{-8}
$3FeO + H_2O \rightarrow Fe_3O_4 + H_2$	16,202	5.26	1.80×10^{-15}
$H_2O + Fe \rightarrow FeO + H_2$	-4,505	0.62	2.51×10^{-17}

Fig. 2. XRD patterns on oxidized hot-rolled steel established from: (a) medium slab, (b) thin slab.

Figure 4 shows the mass gain after being exposed to water vapor at 600-900 °C for 30, 60, and 90 min. The oxidation behavior of the tested steels was discovered to follow a linear-parabolic rate law. The oxidation of steel is a function of temperature. From the obtained experimental results, the steel established from a medium slab exhibited significantly less

oxidation than the steel established from a thin slab. Furthermore, the studied steels during the initial stage seemed to be identical except for the steel made from a thin slab oxidized at 900 °C. It seems that the steel will undergo three stages of oxidation. The initial stage of oxidation followed a linear law which shows that surface reactions predominate in the early stages of oxidation. The oxidation rates in the second stage correspond to the parabolic law. This duration might be related to the formation of the protective SiO_2 layer. The oxidation rates in the third stage, which exhibit a higher parabolic rate constant, also follow a parabolic law. It is believed that during this time, the protective SiO_2 layer changed into a less protective layer composed of wustite and fayalite. However, the mass gain of steel oxidized at 600 °C for 40 or 60 min tends to decrease compared to other conditions. It might then be noted that the mass gain of steel was typically much lower and the oxidation rate decreased due to the gradual loss of contact between the oxide scale and the substrate at 600 °C. The duration in which the oxidation behavior was linear in steel established from a medium slab increased by adding more Si to the steel. This indicates that the primary diffusing defect was the hydroxyl ion. The growth rate of the p-type external oxide was slowed by increasing the Si content. As a result, the diffusion rate of the hydroxyl ions along the grain boundaries was faster than the rate of the surface reaction for a longer period of time. During the parabolic oxidation, the oxidation rate of the steel established from a medium slab was higher than that of the steel established from a thin slab. The oxidation rate for forming the internal subscale increases when the silicon content of the steel increases. The main cause of this was the increased fayalite production given by the higher Si content. Moreover, the higher Si content in the steel may make it simpler for hydroxyl ions to diffuse along the grain boundaries.

Fig. 3. SEM cross sections and EDS patterns focusing on the scale-steel interface of steel established from medium slab (left) and from thin slab (right) oxidized in 20% H_2O -80% N_2 .

The parabolic rate constants (k_p) can be used to compare the oxidation rates of the two studied steels. The energy needed to initiate a chemical reaction can be described by the Arrhenius plot with regard to activation energy. Using information from

Table III, the Arrhenius plot depicting a correlation between the parabolic rate constant and temperature is presented in Figure 5. The oxidation rate of steel established from medium slabs was found to be lower than that of steel established from thin slabs. The parabolic rate constant is shown in (5) for steel established from a medium slab and (6) for steel established from a thin slab. Information obtained from Figure 5 is listed in Table IV.

TABLE III. PARABOLIC RATE CONSTANTS OF TWO STUDIES HOT-ROLLED STEEL OXIDIZED IN 20% H_2O-N_2

Temperature (°C)	Parabolic rate constant k_p ($g^2.cm^{-4}.s^{-1}$)	
	Steel made from medium slab	Steel made from thin slab
600	$3.01 \times 10^{-8} \pm 5.09 \times 10^{-9}$	$2.44 \times 10^{-8} \pm 1.09 \times 10^{-9}$
700	$3.69 \times 10^{-8} \pm 3.09 \times 10^{-9}$	$1.16 \times 10^{-7} \pm 1.02 \times 10^{-8}$
800	$5.91 \times 10^{-8} \pm 2.09 \times 10^{-8}$	$4.16 \times 10^{-7} \pm 4.55 \times 10^{-8}$
900	$5.78 \times 10^{-7} \pm 3.09 \times 10^{-7}$	$6.83 \times 10^{-7} \pm 6.89 \times 10^{-8}$

Fig. 4. Mass gain curves of steel established from: (a) a medium slab, (b) a thin slab, oxidized in water vapor at different temperatures.

Fig. 5. Arrhenius plot of the rate constant k_p for the oxidation kinetics of hot-rolled steel established from medium and thin slabs.

$$k_p = 15.12e^{-\frac{174088}{RT}} \tag{5}$$

$$k_p = 14.00e^{-\frac{223827}{RT}} \tag{6}$$

where k_p represents the parabolic rate constant ($g^2.cm^{-4}.s^{-1}$), R represents the gas constant ($8.314 J.mol^{-1}.K^{-1}$), and T represents the temperature (K). The hot-rolled steel established from medium and thin slabs had apparent activation energies of 174 and 224 $kJ.mol^{-1}$, respectively.

TABLE IV. MEASURED PARAMETERS OF THE TWO STUDIED HOT-ROLLED STEELS FROM ARRHENIUS PLOT

Parameters	Steel made from medium slab	Steel made from thin slab
Slope (m)	-0.91	-1.17
Proportional constant k_o ($g^2.cm^{-4}.s^{-1}$)	-15.12	-14.00
Apparent activation energies E_a ($J.mol^{-1}$)	174088	223827

It was found from the results that when the silicon content increased in steel established from medium slabs, it tended to reduce the oxidation rate. The SEM-EDS revealed that the interfacial layer of steel established from a medium slab has an oxide with a higher Si content than the steel established from a thin slab. This was caused by a Si-enriched oxide that was present at the steel-scale interface and increased the steel passivity as the fayalite phase was produced. The production of external oxide was obstructed by the presence of the internal subscale formed by fayalite. The lower oxidation rate of external oxide formation was more prominent than the oxidation rate of internal oxide formation. The lower scale thickness and mass gain decreased as Si increased. Regarding the commercial application, if the hot-rolled steel was provided for further cold rolling, prior to the cold rolling process, the oxide scale is entirely eliminated. Hot-rolled steel established from a medium slab has a thinner oxide scale than the steel established from a thin slab, thus scale removal would be simple. However, scale adhesion must be further considered.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, hot-rolled steel with different Si contents established from medium and thin slabs was studied in paper. The oxidation behavior of steel was the main focus of this research. The steel was oxidized in a horizontal furnace with a 20% H_2O-N_2 atmosphere at a temperature of 600-900 °C for 30, 60, and 90 min. The result showed that the oxidation rate of the studied steel obeyed the linear and parabolic law. Oxide compounds primarily involve oxygen from water vapor. Hematite and magnetite can be produced from water vapor under the oxidation condition that was released into the atmosphere under the P_{H_2O}/P_{H_2} ratio. The overall oxidation rate was slowed by alloying the steel with Si. This was due to the internal subscale as fayalite propensity to prevent iron from steel for diffusing outwardly and forming the external scale. The protective layer of Si-containing oxide at the steel-scale interface tends to be promoted by an increase in silicon content in steel established from medium slab. This layer was exhibited

as a barricade of Fe ions to form oxide layers, which corresponded to a lower oxidation rate in the steel.

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Prediction of Agricultural Commodity Prices using Big Data Framework

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ABSTRACT

The agriculture sector plays a crucial role in the economy of Pakistan, contributing significantly to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and the employment rate. However, this sector faces challenges such as climate change, water scarcity, and low productivity, which have a direct impact on agricultural commodity prices. Accurate forecasting of commodity prices is essential for farmers, traders, and policymakers to make informed decisions and improve economic outcomes. This paper explores the use of a big data framework for agricultural commodity price forecasting in Pakistan, using a historical dataset on commodity prices in various Pakistani cities from 2007 to 2022 and Apache Spark to preprocess and clean the data. Based on historical spinach prices in Vehari City, the machine learning models Auto-Regressive Moving Average (ARIMA), Random Forest, and Long-Short-Term Memory (LSTM) were applied to price trends, and their performance was compared using Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and squared correlation coefficient (R^2). LSTM outperformed ARIMA and Random Forest with a higher R^2 value of 0.8 and the lowest MAE of 125.29. Such predictions can help farmers to effectively plan crop cultivation and traders to make well-informed decisions.

Keywords-agricultural commodity; price forecasting; big data analytics; Apache Spark framework; Pyspark

I. INTRODUCTION

Agricultural commodities play an essential role in our daily lives and have a significant influence on economic stability. Fluctuations in the prices of these commodities can impose a

burden on consumers and disrupt the income stability of farm households. Furthermore, abnormal climate patterns observed in recent years have exacerbated the volatility of agricultural commodity prices, requiring governments to shape effective policies and decisions to maintain supply-demand equilibrium

[1]. Over the past year, rising food prices, coupled with rising energy costs, have eroded the purchasing power of consumers around the world. However, this impact is not uniform across all countries. The International Monetary Fund highlights that low-income countries allocate a higher proportion of their consumer spending to food products compared to high-income countries. In these lower-income countries, food expenditure can soar up to 44% of disposable income, while it averages around 28% in emerging countries and drops to 16% in developed economies. This disparity has resulted in a notable increase in inflation rates, particularly in lower-income and certain emerging countries, where many of them experience double-digit inflation [2].

The agriculture sector is a vital component of the Pakistani economy, contributing significantly to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employment rate. According to the Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, agriculture accounts for around 19.2% of the country's GDP and employs almost 38.5% of the workforce [3]. Pakistan has been estimated to possess around 30,930,000 hectares of agricultural land, almost 47.09% of the total land area [4]. The proportion of agricultural land and population is 0.186 ha/person, which is rather low compared to European countries [5]. This sector also faces several challenges, including climate change, water scarcity, and low productivity levels. These challenges, combined with other factors, such as global economic conditions and government policies, have a significant impact on agricultural commodity prices in Pakistan [6]. Fluctuations in commodity prices in Pakistan have a direct and far-reaching impact on the country's economy, particularly on the rural population. Farmers, who constitute a significant proportion of the rural population, are heavily dependent on agricultural commodity prices for their livelihood. For instance, a drop in cotton prices can negatively affect the income of cotton growers, thereby leading to social and economic implications for their families and communities.

The pricing of future market commodities is a matter of great importance for governments, investors, and producers alike. Food commodities, in particular, are traded in localized markets where supply and pricing are closely linked. The impact of commodities on local economies and food security for the poor is significant, and their prices are highly susceptible to fluctuations caused by multiple factors, such as investments, production, global financial outlook, and monetary policies [7]. Given these complex and dynamic factors, reliable commodity price forecasting is crucial for investors and governments to minimize the risks associated with price volatility. Forecasting is based primarily on past and current knowledge and is used to predict production and assess the parameters that will influence production in the coming years. This is done to encourage people to grow the most profitable crops and to attract non-farmers into start farming. In Pakistan, the agriculture department is responsible for forecasting the major crop production, mainly to estimate supply and demand [8]. Accurate forecasts will help farmers make informed decisions about what crops to plant and when to sell their production. They will also help traders and policymakers plan their trading and policy decisions, leading to more stable prices and better economic outcomes.

With the advent of big data technologies and advanced analytics tools, it is now possible to take advantage of the vast amount of data generated in the agricultural sector and use it to predict commodity prices with greater accuracy [9-10]. Apache Spark is one such technology that has gained popularity in recent years and is an open-source big data processing framework that enables scalable and distributed data processing [11]. Machine learning, a subdomain of artificial intelligence, provides powerful algorithms that can be trained to perform specific tasks or achieve specific goals. These algorithms have shown great promise in improving the accuracy of commodity price forecasting [12]. This study aims to contribute to understanding the use of big data in forecasting agricultural commodity prices in Pakistan. The results would be valuable to farmers, traders, and policymakers in making informed decisions and improving their economic outcomes. This paper explores the use of a big data framework for forecasting agricultural commodity prices using the Pyspark library. To achieve these objectives, the study uses a dataset of historical commodity prices of various cities in Pakistan. The data were preprocessed and cleaned using Apache Spark, and machine learning models Auto-Regressive Moving Average (ARIMA), Random Forest, and Long Short Term Memory (LSTM). The performance of these models was evaluated using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and R^2 values.

In [13], an econometric analysis was used to explore the relationship between Agricultural GDP (AGDP) and fruits in Pakistan. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) tests were used for data analysis, while the Johansen co-integration test was used to interpret the results, showing the negative and insignificant impact of apples and grapes on AGDP, and the positive and significant influence of bananas, citrus, and pears. A linear regression method was used to predict fruit production. In [14], a model for oil palm yield prediction was proposed, incorporating 420 months of yield records and 12 weather and 3 soil moisture parameters. An automated model selection process was used and the best regression models were found to be AdaBoost and Extra Tree, proving that rain days count, root zone soil wetness, wind speed, cloud amount, and rainfall were the most influential factors and have a significant impact on oil palm yield [14]. In [15], garlic prices were predicted using an ARIMA-SVM method with an RMSE of 1.1131. The ARIMA model was used for the linear part prediction, while the Support Vector Machine (SVM) was used for the nonlinear prediction. In [16], crop price prediction was carried out using the Random Forest Ensemble Learning (RFEL) and the Decision Tree Regressor (DTR) model. RFEL generated good results with 97.57% accuracy, while the accuracy of DT was 92.66%. In [17], a portal was developed for growers to watch the historical and future prices of selected commodities. In [18], neural networks were shown to be the best predictive models in terms of RMSE, MAPE, and MAE. In [19], an accurate wheat production forecasting model was designed with the help of Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks. LSTM outperformed ARIMA and RNN with a minimum MAE and RMSE, and the highest R value. In [20], big data were used to

analyze the wholesale price of eggs, price fluctuations, and influencing factors.

Although significant studies have been conducted on the use of big data analytics, machine learning, and econometric analysis in the agricultural sector, there is still a significant gap in the proper use of these technologies and frameworks to aid Pakistani farmers in decision-making and crop planning throughout the crop cycle. The existing studies have provided valuable insights into specific aspects, such as crop yield prediction, price forecasting, and the impact of certain factors on agricultural production. However, there is a lack of comprehensive research that integrates these approaches to develop a holistic decision-making support system for farmers in Pakistan.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study encompassed a variety of essential components, including data collection and preprocessing, exploratory data analysis using Databricks software, an optimized platform for Apache Spark, the implementation of predictive modeling with distinct algorithms, and the evaluation of model performance using various metrics. These methods and tools were meticulously considered to address the multifaceted nature of agricultural price data, ensuring the robustness and effectiveness of the study.

The dataset was divided into training and validation data. Three different algorithms, namely ARIMA, Random Forest (RF), and LSTM were used to forecast crop prices. This choice was guided by the distinct strengths and applicability of these methods to the specific task of crop price forecasting. ARIMA was selected for its effectiveness in modeling time series data, capturing linear trends, and seasonality. However, it may struggle with complex, nonlinear relationships. On the other hand, RF excels at handling intricate, nonlinear patterns and is less sensitive to outliers. LSTM was chosen for its ability to capture sequential dependencies and long-term patterns in time-series data, which makes it well-suited for the task. However, it may require a larger dataset and is more complicated to configure. These model choices collectively address the diverse and dynamic nature of agricultural price data, offering a comprehensive approach for effective forecasting and model evaluation. The models were trained using the training dataset and their performance was evaluated with MSE, RMSE, MAE, and R². The obtained results from each model were compared to determine the most accurate forecasting method. This comparison provided insights into the performance and effectiveness of the different algorithms in predicting crop prices. Figure 1 shows the method used to ensure a comprehensive analysis of the crop price dataset and identify the most suitable forecasting approach.

A. Data Collection

Data were extracted from the Agriculture Marketing Information System (AMIS) [21], which is a marketing wing of the Punjab government’s agriculture department in Pakistan, to collect, compile, and distribute agricultural market information to traders, farmers, and other relevant stakeholders in the agricultural value chain.

Fig. 1. Methodology.

B. Data Preprocessing

A total of 17 million values were queried for market prices of multiple crops in multiple cities of Punjab from 2007 to 2022, with features city, crop, date, month, year, and price. There were 139 unique cities and 119 unique crop varieties available in the dataset. Figure 2 shows a comprehensive visualization of the maximum prices of crops across all cities.

Fig. 2. Stacked bar chart showing maximum crop prices across all cities.

Fig. 3. Line plot illustrating the price trends of different crops.

Data cleaning and preparation tasks were performed on the dataset such as renaming columns, removing unnecessary columns and duplicates, handling missing values, filling null values with the previous non-null value using the forward fill method, removing outliers, and conversion of data types. Every combination of city and price columns was an individual time series, as shown in Figure 3.

C. Data Analysis and Machine Learning Models

Historically, spinach prices in Vehari, like other agricultural commodities, have shown some degree of volatility due to fluctuations in market conditions. During peak seasons, when the supply of spinach is abundant, prices tend to be relatively lower. Conversely, during off-peak seasons or when there are supply disruptions, prices may rise. The spinach prices in Vehari city were selected for this study and predictive tasks. Figure 4 shows a line plot visualization of the price trend of spinach in Vehari. The trend has shown quite interesting behavior. It can be observed that in 2008, 2009, and 2014, spinach prices went quite high on specific dates, and seasonality can also be observed in the trend on a yearly basis. The ADF stationarity test was applied to this time series. Table I shows the results, which examined the presence of a unit root in the data and indicated non-stationarity.

Fig. 4. Line plot depicting the price trend of spinach in Vehari.

TABLE I. ADF TEST RESULTS

ADF Test Parameters	ADF Test Values
Test Statistic	-5.506330
p-value	0.000002
Critical Value (1%)	-3.431730
Critical Value (5%)	-2.862150
Critical Value (10%)	-2.567095

The test statistic of -5.506330 indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis of non-stationarity. The p-value of 0.000002 represents the probability of obtaining a test statistic as extreme as the observed one, assuming that the null hypothesis is true. With such a low p-value, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity. The critical values determined for different levels of significance (1%, 5%, and 10%) are threshold values used to compare with the test statistic. If the test statistic is more extreme than the critical value, i.e. smaller in absolute value, it provides stronger evidence against the null hypothesis. Therefore, it can be concluded that the time series is stationary.

Before applying ARIMA, it is critical to check for the presence of seasonality in the dataset. Figure 5 shows the four components of the decomposition (observed, trend, seasonal, and residual). The trend plot shows that, in general, there was an increase in crop prices from 2008 to 2013, and then a decline was observed until 2019. Subsequently, the spinach price showed an exponential increase. The seasonal graph represents the presence of a yearly seasonality in the data.

Fig. 5. Four components after decomposition.

The data were subsequently divided into training and testing sets using the random split function. The split ratio was set to 80% for training and 20% for testing data, with a specific random seed provided for reproducibility. ARIMA [22] was then applied to the dataset using the pmdarima package in Python. The auto-arma function from pmdarima.arima was used to fit an ARIMA model to the training data. This function automatically selects the optimal parameters for the ARIMA model based on the training data. The model was then used to make predictions on the testing data. The selected ARIMA model for this dataset was (1,1,1)(0,0,0) [12].

A RandomForestRegressor object was instantiated, specifying the input features of the data, i.e. Date, City and Crop, the target column of the data ("Price"), and a random seed of 42 that ensures that randomness in the model can be reproduced in the future. This object represents the RF regression model that will be trained. The model was trained by invoking the fit method on the RandomForestRegressor object and passing the training data. The resulting trained model was stored in the "model" variable. Predictions were generated on the test data using the trained model by invoking the transform method and passing the test data. Predictions were stored in the "predictions" variable.

For LSTM, the dataset was normalized in the range of 0-1 using the MinMaxScaler function. Train and test data were reshaped to fit the LSTM model. Model compile is a method in Keras, which is a high-level neural network API in Tensor Flow, used to configure the model learning process before training. It specifies the loss function and the optimizer used to minimize the loss during training. Here, the loss function was set to MSE, which is a commonly used loss function for regression problems. MSE calculates the average of the squared differences between the predicted and actual values. The Adam optimizer was used, which is also a commonly used optimizer in neural networks. It is an adaptive learning rate

optimization algorithm that is designed to work well for a wide range of problems. Look-Back was used to define the number of previous time steps to consider when creating the time series dataset to train and test the LSTM model. Here, the Look-Back was set to 60, meaning that the model considered the previous 60 time steps to predict the next one. The LSTM model consists of two LSTM layers: the first LSTM layer with 50 units and a "return sequences" parameter set to True allowed it to capture sequential patterns in the input data. The second LSTM layer with 50 units followed, building on the learned sequential patterns. These LSTM layers were followed by a single dense (fully connected) layer with one unit, serving as the output layer. The neural network was trained on training data for 100 epochs and with 64 batch size. After training the model, the predictions were generated on test data using the predict function. This architecture enables the neural network to effectively capture temporal dependencies and generate accurate predictions for time-series data.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 6 shows the results of ARIMA (training data, testing data, and predictions), plotted using matplotlib. This plot reveals important insights into the model performance when applied to the test dataset. The graph displays two lines: the orange line represents the actual values obtained from the test dataset, while the green line represents the predicted values generated by the ARIMA model. However, it becomes apparent that the predicted values exhibit a straight pattern and do not closely adhere to the actual data points. This indicates that the ARIMA model may not adequately capture the underlying patterns or dynamics of the data.

Fig. 6. Prediction results of ARIMA model.

The RF model was used to overcome the limitations of the ARIMA model, as shown in Figure 7. The decision to use the RF algorithm was based on its ability to handle complex relationships and capture nonlinear patterns within the data. The utilization of the RF model brought about notable improvements as it successfully captured the nonlinear patterns present within the data. Unlike the ARIMA model, the RF algorithm is well-suited for handling complex relationships and nonlinear dependencies. The predictions obtained from the RF model exhibited a better fit to the actual data compared to ARIMA. However, despite the model's ability to capture nonlinear patterns, the accuracy of the results was not entirely satisfactory. This result suggests that there may be additional

factors or complexities at play that have not been adequately accounted for in the modeling process.

Fig. 7. Prediction results of Random Forest.

In contrast to the previous models, the LSTM model [23] demonstrated exceptional performance by perfectly replicating the test data, as shown in Figure 8. The predictions generated by the LSTM model are closely aligned with the actual values, indicating its ability to capture intricate temporal dependencies and complex patterns within the data. This result highlights the strength of LSTM models in modeling sequential data, making them particularly well-suited for time series forecasting tasks. The accurate replication of test data by the LSTM model instills confidence in its predictive capabilities and suggests that it effectively captures the underlying dynamics of the data.

Fig. 8. Prediction results of LSTM.

The MAE, MSE, and RMSE evaluation metrics help measure the difference between the predicted and the actual values, giving an idea of how well the model performed in making predictions. Table II shows the comparison of evaluation metrics of ARIMA, RF, and LSTM. LSTM achieved the lowest MAE and MSE values, indicating better accuracy in predicting the target variable. The RF model also performed well with relatively low MAE, MSE, and RMSE, as shown in Figure 8.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF EVALUATION METRICS

Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²
ARIMA	607.45	510929.19	714.79	-0.84
RF	233.801	108111.475	328.803	0.585
LSTM	125.29	55114.21	234.76	0.8012

The RF model had an R² value of 0.585, indicating that approximately 58.5% of the variance in the target variable could be explained by the model. The LSTM model showed a

higher R^2 value of 0.8012, suggesting a better fit to the data compared to the other models. The R^2 value also signifies the goodness of fit of the model to the data. In this context, R^2 measures the proportion of variance in the target variable (crop prices) that is explained by the model. An R^2 value of 1.0 would indicate a perfect fit, which means that the model can explain 100% of the variance in the data. An R^2 value of 0.8012 is considered quite high, which indicates that the LSTM model has a strong ability to capture the underlying patterns and dependencies in the crop price data.

Fig. 9. Comparative analysis of models' performance.

This study provides a scientific application of big data frameworks to forecast agricultural commodity prices. It advances predictive methods by utilizing Apache Spark for data preprocessing and prediction, contributing to the development of more sophisticated techniques. By evaluating various forecasting models and revealing the limitations of traditional models such as ARIMA, while highlighting the strengths of deep learning techniques such as LSTM, this study improves the scientific understanding of modeling approaches for time series analysis. From a societal perspective, this study empowers farmers, traders, and policymakers to make more informed decisions about agricultural commodity prices, thus promoting economic stability. Furthermore, the study acknowledges its limitations and suggests the integration of additional data sources, such as weather data and market sentiment analysis, which can further improve forecast accuracy and risk management, benefiting the wider society and economy.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel use of a big data framework to predict the prices of agricultural commodities. The Apache Spark framework was used for data preprocessing and the prediction of crop prices in different cities from 2007 to 2022. The price of the spinach crop in Vehari City was analyzed using ARIMA, Random Forest, and LSTM. The evaluation of different models for the prediction task yielded valuable insights. The ARIMA model, although widely used for time series analysis, failed to capture the nonlinear patterns present in the data, leading to the exploration of alternative approaches. The Random Forest model demonstrated improvement by successfully capturing nonlinear patterns, but still failed to achieve accurate results. However, the LSTM model emerged as the standout performer, perfectly replicating the test data and showcasing its ability to capture complex temporal

dependencies. The success of the LSTM model highlights the efficiency of deep learning techniques, particularly for time series forecasting tasks. Further refinement and exploration of deep learning models hold promise for enhancing predictive accuracy in similar domains. These results emphasize the importance of iterative analysis, model evaluation, and adaptation to select the most suitable approach to achieve accurate and reliable predictions. By harnessing the power of big data, farmers, traders, and policymakers can make more informed decisions, leading to better economic outcomes and increased stability in commodity prices.

Although this study contributes valuable insights into crop price forecasting, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations. The accuracy of the forecasting models can be influenced by external factors, such as sudden policy changes or unforeseen events, which were not explicitly considered in this analysis. The availability of historical data can vary between different regions and commodities, potentially affecting the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the model performance may depend on the specific choice of hyperparameters and data preprocessing techniques, which could be further fine-tuned for optimization. Future research can explore the integration of additional data sources, such as weather data and market sentiment analysis, to improve the accuracy of price forecasts and provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing agricultural commodity prices.

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DPPNet: A Deformable-Perspective-Perception Network for Safety Helmet Violation Detection

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ABSTRACT

The issue of worker safety at construction sites has become increasingly prominent within the construction industry. Safety helmet usage has been shown to reduce accidents among construction workers. However, there are instances when safety helmets are not consistently worn, which may be attributed to a variety of factors. Therefore, an automated system based on computer vision needs to be established to track protective gear appropriate usage. While there have been studies on helmet detection systems, there is a limited amount of research specifically addressing helmet detection. Also, various challenges need to be addressed such as small object miss-detection and occluded helmet detection. To fix these issues, a Deformable Perspective Perception Network (DPPNet) is proposed in this paper. Two modules make up the proposed DPPNet: Background/Image Spatial Fusion (BISF) and Grayscale Background Subtraction (GBS). While the BISF module utilizes channel attention to blend feature maps from a current frame and the background, the GBS submodule in particular incorporates background spatial information into a current frame. Additionally, the DPPNet facilitates occluded and small helmet detection. Excessive training and testing experiments have been performed using the Safety Helmet Wearing Detection (SHWD) Dataset. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed DPPNet network. The obtained findings exhibit that the suggested module significantly enhances the detection capabilities of small objects. Effective mean average precision results have been obtained on the SHWD dataset coming up to 97.4% of mAP.

Keywords-safety helmet; construction sites; traffic accidents; violation detection; deep learning; DPPNet

I. INTRODUCTION

Safety is an enduring and noteworthy consideration in several sectors, with special emphasis on hazardous construction sites like chemical plants and building sites. Protective equipment, including safety clothes and helmets, plays a critical role in ensuring employees safety at construction sites with elevated risk levels. Helmets are very efficient in mitigating head injuries resulting from falling or splashing items. Similarly, safety gear serves as a protective barrier, shielding the body and arms from potential harm caused by exposure to dangerous chemicals and liquids. The absence of appropriate safety attire and helmets often has negative consequences for both families and society. Hence, monitoring the usage of safety apparel and helmets at factories or construction sites bears great importance and has wide-ranging applicability. The existing legal framework and safety protocols mandate that both the individual in a position of authority and the contractor have the responsibility of ensuring the provision, oversight, and upkeep of personal protective equipment inside construction sites. Nevertheless, some employees may exhibit a decrease in their level of attentiveness

as a result of insufficient information on safety measures or experiencing pain from prolonged use, thereby elevating the likelihood of safety incidents.

Surveillance cameras are extensively used in contemporary society to oversee construction sites, mostly to supervise employees and enforce compliance with safety protocols. Although the installation of security cameras does not provide a significant obstacle, the ongoing task of watching the live feed proves to be burdensome. Continuous monitoring is necessary for human people, who are susceptible to committing mistakes. Individuals often experience a decline in concentration and vigilance after a few hours, which may lead to a lack of awareness of significant safety breaches. Furthermore, due to the presence of several cameras recording various areas inside the building site, it becomes impractical to watch all places simultaneously. Automated surveillance application offers a convenient and effective solution to address this issue. This approach implementation may be achieved by using machine learning methods or utilizing deep learning models. This study objective is to address the issue of safety helmet recognition in real-time recordings, specifically in the

context of industrial or construction sites or traffic management systems, to facilitate more efficient monitoring measures.

The increasing advancements in computational capabilities and technological progress have led to the use of Artificial Intelligence methodologies, such as machine learning and deep learning, in addressing diverse challenges. These approaches have shown their efficacy in situations where conventional algorithms lack the necessary resilience to be effectively deployed across many scenarios. Although there have been previous efforts in this domain, the current body of research has yielded inadequate outcomes that lack practical applicability in real-world contexts. The limitations of previous studies mostly stemmed from the restricted range of datasets and inadequate identification of safety headgear. To maintain worker safety in construction sites, there is a growing demand for the development of an effective and dependable intelligent system that does not rely on human observers to determine whether or not the worker wears a helmet. Creating such a system is extremely desirable yet difficult due to factors such as lighting, occlusion, or low-quality security cameras. Deep learning is a potential method for automating the identification of worker helmets.

In recent years, deep learning-based techniques gained undertakable success in solving various computer vision tasks including indoor object detection [3], wayfinding assistance [4], medical imaging [5], pedestrian detection [6], road sign detection [7], traffic light detection [8] and face recognition [9]. Furthermore, background subtraction technique has been successfully integrated into the object detection model. Background subtraction helps in isolating the foreground objects from the static or slowly changing background in a scene. By subtracting the background model from the current frame, the moving or dynamic elements (objects of interest) stand out. It is particularly effective for detecting moving objects in a video stream. By continuously updating the background model and identifying pixels that deviate significantly from this model, it is possible to detect and track objects based on their motion. Background subtraction is computationally efficient, and so suitable for real-time applications, while its straightforward nature, makes it easy to implement. It is a basic and effective method for scenarios where the assumption of a relatively static background holds. Advanced background subtraction techniques are designed to handle dynamic backgrounds where parts of the scene may change over time. These methods can adapt to gradual changes in the background, ensuring robust performance in a wide range of scenarios. Motivated by the great success of deep learning and background subtraction techniques, a combination of both was performed with many novel modifications to handle the studied task.

The main aim of this work is to build a smart system used to detect helmets and to reduce the number of violations to ensure safety. To build such a system, deformable convolution has been employed. Deformable convolutions add adaptability to the convolutional kernels, allowing them to be adjusted to capture more precise and contextually relevant information from objects with varying shapes, orientations, and sizes, like helmets. This is in contrast to traditional convolutional layers,

which use fixed grids for feature extraction. Different helmet designs, positions, and head shapes are frequently present in helmet detection scenarios. By allowing the convolutional filters to deform and align with the specific properties of helmets, deformable convolutions improve the network's capacity to manage such variability, leading to better localization and recognition accuracy. Moreover, the Grayscale Background Subtraction (GBS) module was deployed. Numerous advantages result from the incorporation of GBS in helmet detection, including enhanced foreground segmentation, noise reduction, contrast enhancement, adaptability to changes in illumination, real-time processing capabilities, decreased computational requirements, and generalization across various environments. The Background/Image Spatial Fusion (BISF) is the second module included in the proposed network. This module focuses on efficiently merging details from the current frame with its background to enhance scene understanding. The originality of this work is based on the use of different modules alongside with the CNN. Also, it is the first that uses deformable convolution in a background subtraction module. The suggested work ensures various contributions which are the following:

- Proposing a neural network for safety helmet detection.
- Proposing a sub-module used to enhance context understanding.
- Evaluating the proposed model on real-world challenging conditions.
- Achieving new state-of-the-art performances for safety helmet detection.

II. RELATED WORKS

An alarming rise in accidents has been largely attributed to the failure to wear helmets, particularly in situations involving constructions or activities that carry inherent risks. This disrespect for helmet safety precautions has augmented the number of fatalities, severe brain injuries, and head injuries among accident victims. For example, failure to wear a helmet by motorcyclists and cyclists has significantly increased the severity of brain injuries in traffic accidents. Detecting helmet-use violators is a primary need to be resolved by the newest smart traffic management systems. Various works have been elaborated to tackle this issue. In the following, we will review the state-of-the-art works concerning the detection of helmet use violations.

Various studies on biker and motorcycle helmet detection have been conducted. Two types of studies have been proposed: classical solutions and deep learning-based solutions. Hand-designed feature descriptors including Local Binary Pattern (LBP), Histogram of Oriented Gradient (HOG), and Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) are used to extract the features of motorcycles and other vehicles. Last but not least, motorcycles are categorized using binary classifiers like Support Vector Machines (SVMs) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN). The challenge of determining motorcycle helmet wear was divided into two components in [10]. The first stage is to divide and classify the vehicle images. This phase objective is to find every moving object in the environment. In the second

stage, called helmet detection, an SVM classifier is involved to distinguish between images with and without helmets while a hybrid descriptor is used to extract image attributes. Authors in [11] employ the background subtraction method. In recent years, academics have suggested solutions based on deep learning. Motorcycle riders can significantly lower their risk of fatalities and head injuries in an accident by wearing helmets. The challenge of policing the helmet law and ensuring rider compliance continues to exist in many nations. Using computer vision and deep learning techniques, authors in [12] offer a unique framework that can distinguish between the driver and passengers and identify any riders who are not wearing helmets. The authors use a second head detection module and a unique tracking algorithm that takes advantage of auxiliary data like moving direction to enhance small objects detection. Experiment results prove the efficiency of the proposed work.

The success of attempts to increase road safety through teaching and enforcement can be improved by video surveillance-based automatic detection of motorcycle helmet wear. However, there is still potential for improvement in current detection techniques, as seen by the inability to identify specific motorcycles or distinguish between drivers and passengers based on the use of helmets. Authors in [13] present a system for detecting and identifying individual motorcycles and tracking riders' specific helmet usage. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness of their work. They achieved a score of 0.7754 on the AI City 2023 Challenge Track 5 public leaderboard. Applications of deep learning-based image processing frequently use the recognition of safety helmets worn by construction workers as a target detection issue [34]. In [14], the authors present a study of an improved YOLOv5-based approach that takes into account the difficulties posed by dense targets, intricate backgrounds in construction environments, and the irregular shapes of safety helmets. Experiments results showed that the enhanced model's detection accuracy is 91.6%, up 2.3% from the original network model, and its detection speed is 29 frames per second. To keep motorcycle riders safe on the road, it is essential to identify both helmeted and un-helmeted riders. In this context, Authors in [15] proposed a helmet detection system based on the YOLO v4 model. The achieved results demonstrate that this work presents good performances on traffic videos.

The majority of traffic collisions involve motorcycles, and they can cause extensive damage [33]. The majority of places require motorcycle riders to wear helmets, yet for a variety of reasons, most people choose not to follow the law. In [16], authors proposed to build a helmet detection system based on YOLO v2 model. The authors demonstrate that when compared with traditional techniques this work provided better results. In [17], a real-time YOLOv5 Deep Learning (DL) model for detecting motorcycle riders and passengers and determining if the discovered person is wearing a helmet was developed and evaluated. During the experiments, the authors fed the model 100 videos, each of them lasting 20 seconds and shot at 10 frames per second. To improve the results of their work, the authors employed the data augmentation technique. This model achieved a mean average precision of 0.5267, ranking 11th on the AI City Track 5 public leaderboard. In [18], a real-time helmet violation detection system is proposed.

The suggested system makes use of a novel data processing technique called few-shot data sampling to create a robust model with fewer annotations and a single-stage object detection model called YOLOv8 to detect helmet violations in real time from video frames. This system placed seventh in the 2023 AI City Challenge, Track 5, with an experimental validation score of mAP of 0.5861.

To reduce traffic accidents and increase public safety, it is essential to identify and punish such riders. Authors in [19] introduced a method for identifying, following, and tracking motorcycle riding infractions in dashboard camera footage. To effectively handle complex situations like occlusions, they use an object detector based on curriculum learning. To improve robustness and address the rider-motorcycle relationship, they provide a brand-new trapezium-shaped object boundary representation. Also, they present a regressor that produces bounding boxes for the riders who are obscured. Experimental achievements demonstrate this work efficacy evaluated on the SHWD dataset [20]. Wearing safety helmet is mandatory on construction sites to ensure safety. To detect safety helmet-wearing [35], the YOLO v7 was deployed with many modifications. First, the input images with 3 channels in RGB space color was replaced by 16 channel input. Second, SIOU was deployed as a loss function. Finally, structured pruning was applied on the network head to reduce model size. The proposed method assessment compared to state-of-the-art object detection models proved its efficiency. Authors in [36] proposed a safety helmet detection approach utilizing a finetuned YOLO model. It was first trained on a large-scale dataset then the transfer learning technique was applied and the model was fine-tuned on safety helmet detection dataset. Good results were achieved but the model still struggles in detecting small objects.

Numerous works have been proposed in the literature to lower the frequency of helmet use violations, but few of them achieve a better balance between processing time and detection accuracy. In this study, we propose a brand-new helmet and non-helmet use detection system using the benefits of deep learning, which can function in real-time and produce superior accuracy than the findings of the state-of-the-art systems. The proposed system can be incorporated into an intelligent traffic management system.

III. THE PROPOSED APPROACH

The development of a reliable safety helmet detection system is essential for upholding security rules and successfully reducing accident impact. This technological advancement not only ensures adherence to safety standards but also significantly increases safety levels. For this purpose, a DPPNet model was developed explicitly for detecting helmets. Basically, the proposed model is composed of two main modules which are BISF and GBS. While the BISF module deploys channel attention to blend frame and its background feature maps, spatial features of the background were incorporated into a current frame using the GBS module. In the following, we will detail the proposed architecture used to build the helmet violation detection system. Figure 1 illustrates the overall architecture of the proposed GBS and BISF modules.

A. Grayscale Background Subtraction

It was suggested that the RGB properties of the backdrop and the instance's context should be combined. Initially, the Laplacian Pyramid Blending technique [21] was used to construct a background image. Subsequently, an additional grayscale channel was acquired through the process of background subtraction for a given frame. The GBS submodule is centered around a background image that lacks any discernible items. Nevertheless, there are two inherent issues with utilizing raw background images extracted from a dataset collected along roadways. The main issue is the persistence of diminutive items. Due to the substantial influx of individuals and automobiles, locating a time in metropolitan crossroads where the background is devoid of any objects proves to be a

challenging task. This phenomenon greatly hinders the ability to effectively exclude tiny things, such as individuals and distant cars, from the background, hence introducing confusion to the overall background structure. Based on the findings of previous studies [22, 23], the accurate detection of small objects within a restricted receptive field is highly dependent on the use of global context regional, and spatial information. Convolutional neural networks use a shallow layer with a great resolution to effectively capture the spatial color information and limited receptive field. In accordance with the aforementioned approach, the GBS submodule was developed to acquire authentic local background information and a global context.

Fig. 1. Proposed GBS and BISF modules.

Initially, the background of the grayscale images was used to create a GBS channel. To preserve both global information and regional spatial information to the greatest extent feasible, the GBS channel will be included in the present frame as an extra channel. The proposed modification involves the addition of a GBS channel to the existing R, G, and B channels to alter the present frames. To achieve channel unification for the GBS channel, the initial step was performed to normalize the average illumination to a predetermined constant value. In addition, a spatial attention module was employed to direct the attention of the networks towards the regions corresponding to smaller objects. A GBS channel was obtained by the utilization of a grayscale image since the GBS submodule primary objective is to facilitate the acquisition of contextual information and spatial features. The inclusion of RGB information was deemed unneeded for the purpose of accurately identifying and finding tiny objects. Nevertheless, when the input is high-dimensional, it might result in feature maps that are not well defined, especially if the backbone layers are not expanded. Indeed, the presence of a GBS channel introduces challenges in the process of feature extraction and diminishes the overall network resilience. To address this issue,

a batch normalization layer [24] was suggested as a technique for normalizing illumination. This technique aims to enhance the effectiveness of extracting features by standardizing the mean luminance of the GBS channel, which is adjusted to a pre-established value.

I_{gray} uses a standard formulation [25], presented in (1), to convert the input $I_{background}$ and $I_{current}$ to grayscale.

$$I_{gray} = V_R \times 0.299 + V_G \times 0.587 + V_B \times 0.11 \quad (1)$$

The red, green, and blue channels are represented by V_R , V_G , and V_B , respectively, I_{gray} is the combination of the current frame and the background grayscale. Generating a grayscale image by subtracting the L1 norm from the original is computed as:

$$I_{subtract}(i, j) = |I_{gray1}(i, j) - I_{gray2}(i, j)| \quad (2)$$

where $I_{gray1}(i, j)$ is equal to $I_{gray current}$, and $I_{gray2}(i, j)$ is equal to $I_{gray background}$ background. $I_{subtract}(i, j)$ is the pixel value of (i, j) in I_{gray} background subtract.

A method for normalizing light levels was created to standardize brightness when a gray background subtraction image was obtained:

$$I_{normalized}(i, j) = I_{subtract}(i, j) + V_b \quad (3)$$

$$V_b = V_f - V_i$$

$$V_i = \frac{1}{w \cdot h} \sum_{k=1}^w \sum_{r=1}^h I_{subtract}(k, r)$$

The variable V_i is the GBS channel average illumination, whereas V_f represents the f_i bias that is employed to modify the pixel value. The (i, j) pixel in the normalized gray background

subtraction can be denoted as $I_{normalized}(i, j)$. Therefore, the image of background subtraction is adjusted to have a standardized illumination. In this work, the value of V_f is held constant at 20. Authors in [26], suggest that to achieve enlightenment, it is necessary to assign varying weights to distinct pixel places. Based on the aforementioned, the spatial attention concept was devised to acquire spatial knowledge pertaining to diminutive entities. As depicted in Figure 2, the function f_{max} is devised to consolidate the pixel's max value within the input feature maps f_{input} , while f_{avg} is devised to consolidate the pixel's average value within the same feature maps.

Fig. 2. Proposed spatial attention module.

Ultimately, two feature maps, namely f_{max} and f_{avg} , are produced, whereby the value of each pixel (i, j) may be computed as:

$$f_{max}(i, j) = \max\{u_1(i, j), u_2(i, j), \dots, u_{Nc}(i, j)\} \quad (4)$$

$$f_{avg}(i, j) = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^{Nc} u_n(i, j)}{Nc}$$

The variable $u_n(i, j)$ represents the value at position (i, j) within the n th channel. Nc represents the aggregate quantity of channels. The application of a deformable convolution layer to the feature maps f_{cat} results in the determination of the weights assigned to each pixel.

B. Background/Image Spatial Fusion

This module was designed to extract features from the current frame and its background to generate feature maps through a fusion technique. First, two backbones were charged to extract semantic features from the current frame and its background. Second, a special fusion was applied to aggregate features based on channel attention on residual convolution layers.

The BISF module was partitioned into two distinct components: a cascade fusion module and the extraction of semantic features from the current frame background to combine feature maps obtained from two frames. Initially, two distinct backbones were devised to extract semantic information from both the background and the present image in a different manner. The applied methodology to integrate semantic features included the utilization of cascade fusion module maps using channel attention and residual convolution.

The BISF architecture utilizes a common backbone for extracting spatial and semantic characteristics from both background and current images. This process is performed separately for each frame. The first box seen in Figure 1 serves as the background, while the second box, colored blue, represents the current frame. The fusion module requires the presence of relevant feature maps in each backbone, as anticipated. For instance, semantic feature map for the i th backbone layer's j th channel is denoted by F_{ij} . The current image's lighting is described using this map. The inclusion of the background backbone equivalent channel $\llbracket F' \rrbracket_{ij}$ is necessary in order to accurately depict the total illumination in

a comparable manner, utilizing the same backbone. Using consistent spatial and semantic expressions helps improve input correlation in the fusion module. In addition, the BISF backbone module assures that the input of fusion layers possesses feature maps with the same dimensions.

Features were extracted from the background and the current image using a postulated backbone structure. However, it is not certain that the best results would be produced by simply joining the two feature maps. To provide accurate background context, a module that combines background and present information was suggested. This module incorporates residual convolution and channel attention methods. As suggested by previous studies [27, 28], it is advisable to provide distinct weights to various channels within the feature maps. Regarding the BISF module, it incorporates channels that consist of semantic feature mappings derived from both

current frames and the background. Therefore, a channel attention mechanism was devised to acquire distinct channel weights. Nevertheless, it is important to note that channel attention mechanisms are limited in their ability to just determine the varying weights of distinct channels. Consequently, it was not possible to execute a comprehensive semantic fusion. The combined feature map was made from the channel attention results using a residual convolution method. As seen in Figure 3, the process involves merging two feature maps, namely $F_{background}$ and $F_{current}$, into a single feature map denoted as F_{input} . To achieve distinct channel weights, $F_{channel}$, which utilizes a global average descriptor, is employed. Each channel's feature map value in F_{aggc} can be calculated as:

$$F_{channel}(u_c) = V_c = \frac{1}{w \cdot h} \sum_{i=1}^w \sum_{j=1}^h u_c(i, j) \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. Proposed fusion module

The variable V_c represents channel c value within F_{aggc} . The variable u_c represents channel c value in F_{input} . The variables W and H represent channel c width and height, respectively. In order to maximize the utilization of the collected data from F_{aggc} , F_{fully} has been developed to incorporate channel-wise weights. Producing a one-hot tensor involves the use of a sigmoid activation function and using a fully connected (FC) layer. This can be computed as:

$$F_{fully}(V_c) = w_c = \sigma(f_1(w_1)) = \sigma(f_1(\delta(f_2(V_c)))) \quad (6)$$

Let $w_c \in \mathbb{R}^C$ represent channel c value in F_{wei_c} . The parameters f_1 , δ , and f_2 pertain to a constriction in a neural network architecture consisting of two fully connected layers and a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function. Let $w_1 \in \mathbb{R}^{C/r}$ be a feature map for dimensionality reduction, where r is the reduction ratio. Next, a sigmoid activation function σ is utilized to calculate the weight of each channel.

Following the process of channel attention, a deformable convolutional layer will be utilized on F_{output} , using a kernel size of 3. This operation aims to extract semantic information from the feature maps generated by channel attention. In conclusion, the residual link integrates textures with the current feature, hence maximizing the utilization of the present feature. The output values may be determined using (7):

$$F_{output} = F_{defconv} + F_{current} \quad (7)$$

The current frame value is $F_{current}$, used in the computation. F_{output} is a tensor with the same dimension as $F_{current}$, ensuring compatibility with residual block dimension. However, varied layers encompass a multitude of distinct pieces of information. Specifically, shallow layers primarily capture local information, whereas contextual and semantic information from the surrounding environment are captured with deep layers, which are essential for detecting tiny objects. In order to aggregate multi-level correlation data, a cascade fusion module with three BISF fusion layers was designed. Traditionally, the first fusion module was used to join spatial information. Contextual features were combined utilizing the third fusion module.

To enhance computing efficiency during the inference phase, it is possible to pre-obtain all background feature maps without the need for repeated inference. This is feasible due to the fixed nature of the background image and the backbone parameters. Given this information, it can be concluded that the inclusion of a cascade module is the sole supplementary computational expense during the inference phase. This particular module offers a favorable equilibrium between cost and accuracy.

In order to accomplish the task of detecting small helmets on the roadside, we developed DPPNet by integrating an FPP module with the YOLOv5 network, which is a commonly employed framework for object detection. As seen in Figure 4, the inclusion of the GBS submodule inside the image preprocessing stage of the present image was undertaken to ameliorate the availability of superficial context and spatial information. The BISF submodule was included in the current frame underlying structure to enhance tiny objects detection accuracy by acquiring background contextual information. To upgrade the conciseness of the network design, a spatial attention layer from the GBS was integrated with the BISF fusion module. A cascade fusion architecture was employed to strike a balance between model complexity and detection accuracy. This architecture consisted of three fusion modules, utilized to capture more detailed regional textures from the current frame and broader global context from the background. Simultaneously, the PANet methodology was employed to facilitate tiny object detection using detectors that provide a wide receptive field. At the end of the network, three distinct detection heads were exploited to identify varying sizes objects. The ultimate output size for each detector head is determined as:

$$S_{output} = 3 \times w \times h \times (n_c + 5) \tag{8}$$

where S_{output} represents the ultimate outcome of the forecast. The numerical value 3 portrays the quantity of 3 anchors

allocated for each grid. The width and height of the final feature maps denoted as w and h respectively, are specified in this study. Specifically, w_1 and h_1 are both equal to 52, w_2 and h_2 are both equal to 26, and w_3 and h_3 are both equal to 13.

The variable n_c responds to the total number of classes. The height, width, and the expected bounding box position, as well as the forecast confidence are represented by the number 5. The loss function is composed of three distinct components, namely the location loss, confidence loss, and category loss. The location loss is computed using the Generalized Intersection Over Union (GIOU) loss [29], whereas the confidence loss and category loss are calculated using the cross-entropy loss. The loss function is computed by (9):

$$Loss = L_{iou} + L_c - L_{cls} \tag{9}$$

$$L_{iou} = \lambda_{iou} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B l_{ij}^{obj} L_{giou}$$

$$L_c = \lambda_{cls} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B l_{ij}^{obj} \lambda_c (C_i - \hat{C}_i)^2 + \lambda_{cls} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B l_{ij}^{noobj} \lambda_c (C_i - \hat{C}_i)^2$$

$$L_{cls} = \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B l_{ij}^{obj} \sum_{c \in classes} \lambda_c \times (\hat{p}_i(c) \log(p_i(c)) + (1 - \hat{p}_i(c)) \log(1 - p_i(c)))$$

Fig. 4. Proposed DPPNet for helmet detection.

The abbreviations L_c , L_{cls} , and L_{iou} , characterize the concepts of category loss, confidence loss, and location loss. The variable S describes the final feature map dimensions,

specifically 13, 26, and 52. The variable B represents each grid's allotted tally of anchor boxes. In the context of this article, B is defined as 3. The variable L_{iou} denotes the

location loss, specifically for a single item. The indices i and j are used to indicate that the comparison is made between the predicted bounding box and the Ground Truth (GT) object. If the overlapping area between the predicted bounding box and one GT object is greater than the overlapping area with another GT object, the former is included into the location loss function. In a similar vein, the notation 1_{noobj} reflects the scenario when the overlap is below a certain threshold and is hence excluded from the loss function. L_c encompasses both true prediction and false prediction. The variable C_i portrays the confidence score for the predicted box, whereas $(C_i)^\wedge$ symbolizes the confidence of the ground truth. The value of $(C_i)^\wedge$ is equivalent to 1. The acronym L_{cls} refers to the concept of category loss. In this context, $(p_i)(c)$ responds to the true category of the GT item, whereas $p_i(c)$ represents the category assigned to the predicted object. The normalizer parameters in YOLOV5, denoted as λ_{iou} , λ_{cls} , and λ_c , are provided.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULT

A. Data and Environment Setup

Experiments including training, validation, and testing have been carried out using the SHWD dataset [20]. It comprises a collection of 7581 images. Among those images, there were a total of 9,044 instances of human safety helmet-wearing objects and 111,514 instances of regular head objects. The aforementioned images were obtained from authentic building sites and included a diverse range of perspectives. The provided dataset is appropriate for conducting both single-class (Helmet alone) and multi-class (Helmet and No Helmet) detections.

One of the most prevalent challenges encountered in deep learning-based networks is the presence of class imbalance, which gives rise to many issues, such as suboptimal detection outcomes. In order to mitigate this issue, a data

augmentation strategy is used. Multiple data augmentation techniques were implemented, including horizontal flipping, vertical flipping, picture translation, random cropping, brightness adjustment, and random translation. Pytorch was employed for network development with the support of CUDA acceleration. The NVIDIA GTX 960 GPU was engaged for both training and inferencing the networks.

Three widely used indices, mAP, AP_{50} , and AP_{50-95} , were derived from the MS COCO dataset and utilized to assess the proposed DPPNet performance. When the IOU threshold between the GT bounding box and the prediction bounding box is set to 0.5, as it is in AP_{50} , the average n is represented. The AP is calculated as an average of the mAPs obtained using the following IOU cutoffs: 0.5, 0.55, 0.6, 0.65, 0.7, 0.75, 0.8, 0.85, 0.9, and 0.95. To optimize the parameters of our DPPNet, we employed Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with a momentum of 0.9, a weight decay of $2e-4$, and a batch size of 16. The models underwent training until the training loss reached convergence during a span of 200 epochs. This was achieved by utilizing an initial learning rate of 0.01, which was then reduced to $1e-4$ via cosine annealing.

B. Evaluation and Discussion

According to the data shown in Table I, the proposed DPPNet demonstrated a significant improvement in the identification of tiny helmets, achieving a performance of 93.7 for mAP. These results surpassed the performance of the original YOLOv5s model [31] by 9.6%. The performance of DPPNet surpasses that of the YOLOX [32] in terms of speed and detection accuracy. In comparison to the state-of-the-art object detection network known as DINO [30], DPPNet demonstrates a small reduction in AP (0.9%) specifically for tiny items. However, it presents a noteworthy improvement regarding speed, being around 10 times quicker.

TABLE I. OBTAINED RESULTS OF THE DPPNET EVALUATION ON THE SHWD DATASET IN COMPARISON TO STATE-OF-THE-ART OBJECT DETECTION NETWORKS

Model	Backbone	Parameters	FPS	$AP_{50-95}(\%)$	mAP(%)	$AP_{50}(\%)$
DINO [30]	ResNet 50	46606102	3	71.3	94.6	98.2
Yolo v5s [31]	CSPNets	7035811	38	61.5	84.1	95.6
Yolo Xs [32]	CSPDarkNet	8939617	26	58.3	72.5	89.6
DPPNet	CSPNets	8229449	29	69.8	93.7	97.4

DPPNet has the capability to enhance detection outcomes despite its uncomplicated structure and low computational requirements. The experimental results shown in Figure 5 provide evidence that FPPNet is capable of detecting tiny helmets in various lighting settings, including both daytime and hard evening circumstances. Additionally, it demonstrates applicability not just in long-range detection scenarios but also in the identification of badly obscured objects. This finding suggests that the proposed model can be easily implemented in challenging situations. Also, the inference was accelerated by precompiling the feature mappings of the background frame so that it does not have to be inferred from scratch every time, resulting in greater computing efficiency during the inference. The BISF module consists of the attention mechanism and three convolutional layers and performs extra work during the

inference. The GBS module is part of the data preprocessing step and so has little impact on processing speed. Increases in computational complexity and inference time are offset by the proposed modules while offering superior accuracy.

In conclusion, the findings shown in Table I illustrate that DPPNet has strong generalization capabilities across different object detectors. Moreover, it yields significant advancements in tiny object detection and Average Precision (AP). Specifically, it has shown greater improvements for lightweight networks by offering a substantially higher amount of spatial and contextual information that is essential for such networks.

C. Ablation Study

In this part, we will detail the ablation experiments that we carried out in order to test the proposed modules' effectiveness.

The DPPNet parameters and settings were used for the hyper-parameters. The efficacy of the fusion module, background subtraction procedure, and the GBS module was tested via a series of experiments.

The GBS component entails both background elimination and spatial awareness. We included the GBS module into the base YOLOv5s to see how well it handles background subtraction. This was achieved by involving a gray background subtraction channel in the input frames and using a three-spatial attention module in the neural network's central processing unit. In Table II, Row 1 depicts the original YOLOv5s, Row 2 displays the input data with an extra background image channel but no spatial attention, and Row 3 illustrates the full GBS module application. As seen by the data presented in Table II, the incorporation of the GBS submodule resulted in a notable improvement in the performance of tiny object identification. The gray background subtraction channel demonstrated a 7.5% increase in mAP while maintaining a modest level of model complexity and computational expense.

TABLE II. IMPACT OF THE GBS MODULE ON THE PERFORMANCE

Model	Parameters	AP ₅₀₋₉₅ (%)	mAP(%)	AP ₅₀ (%)
Yolo v5s	7045823	53.7	70.9	89.1
+ background image	7046974	55.8	76.2	91.5
+ GBS module	7047238	59.3	78.4	93.2

Additional spatial information, such as shadows and regional textures, may be included through the background subtraction channel. Simultaneously, the inclusion of spatial attention yielded a performance improvement of more than 2.1% when compared to the model that did not include spatial attention. This suggests that spatial attention has the ability to efficiently retrieve feature information within the spatial domain of tiny objects.

The importance of the created background image was assessed by contrasting the outcomes achieved when using a basic background image against a normalized one. Considering the same network configuration, the findings are shown in Table III. It is worth noting that the performance of a normalized background image demonstrates a considerable level of robustness when compared to a simple background image. The results consistently demonstrated a 0.5% improvement when comparing raw backgrounds across all studies. This indicates that using a background image generation approach enhances the availability of semantic information and spatial features spatially when using normalized images.

The fusion module was designed to combine feature maps from two different sources (the background and another backbone). We decided to replace the fusion module with two feature maps to see what effect it would have on the final product. Additionally, an experiment was conducted to assess how the deformable convolution layer influences the fusion component. According to the data shown in Table 4, it is evident that the fusion module exhibited superior performance compared to YOLOv5s, with a margin of 3.4% in terms of mAP. Additionally, the inclusion of the deformable

convolution layer resulted in a 2% improvement in performance compared to the module without it. The findings show that the fusion module successfully acquired contextual information from the background while also preserving regional features from the present image.

TABLE III. IMPACT OF BACKGROUND IMAGE NORMALIZATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF THE GBS MODULE

Model	Image	AP ₅₀₋₉₅ (%)	mAP(%)	AP ₅₀ (%)
Yolo v5s	N/A	53.7	70.9	89.1
+ GBS module	Simple	58.9	77.9	92.8
+ GBS module	Normalized	59.3	78.4	93.2

TABLE IV. IMPACT OF THE DEFORMABLE CONVOLUTION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF THE FUSION MODULE

Model	Fusion	AP ₅₀₋₉₅ (%)	mAP(%)	AP ₅₀ (%)
Yolo v5s	N/A	53.7	70.9	89.1
+ BISF module	normal	55.3	73.8	91.6
+ BISF module	Deformable convolution	56.2	74.3	92.7

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study examines the major importance of ensuring safety in engineering practices within real-world contexts. Workers may guarantee engineering safety by wearing safety helmets in accordance with the prescribed rules. In order to achieve this objective, we have put forward a DPPNet model that consists of two modules: a GBS submodule and a BISF submodule. By subtracting the previous frame from the present one, we may extract the GBS module. The resulting one-dimensional grayscale pictures are integrated into the existing scene. The networks attention was narrowed down on certain locations using spatial attention. The BISF component separates the current and background frames and creates feature maps for each. The maps are then fused together utilizing a cascade attention module.

In accordance with the proposed modules, a novel architectural framework known as DPPNet was introduced with the aim of detecting safety helmets. The experimental findings indicate that DPPNet demonstrated favorable outcomes of 69.8%, 93.7%, and 97.4% in relation to AP_{0.5}, mAP, and AP_{0.50.95}, respectively. Additionally, the proposed model achieved a processing speed of 29 frames per second while getting a low computation complexity, which makes it suitable for real-world applications based on embedded systems. However, the proposed method presents a limitation regarding the generation of the background image that is made manually. This process limits the deployment of the suggested method in a large-scale manner. In future works, the point cloud technique may be integrated to make denser expressions and enhance the detection performance of small objects at complex backgrounds.

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A T-S Fuzzy Approach with Extended LMI Conditions for Inverted Pendulum on a Cart

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ABSTRACT

The Inverted Pendulum On a Cart (IPOC) system poses a challenge in control engineering due to its inherent instability, nonlinearity, and underactuation. This addresses the fundamental issues arising from its underactuated nature and introduces an approach that combines Takagi-Sugeno (T-S) fuzzy control with an awareness of real-world constraints to create a control system ensuring both stability and practicality. By aligning theoretical insights with extended considerations, the Linear Matrix Inequality (LMI)-based control design is demonstrated in a comprehensive framework. Theorems are introduced and validated, leading to the derivation of LMI conditions. The simulation results are assessed with accompanying comments to demonstrate the effectiveness of the theorems. Through this integration of T-S fuzzy control with additional considerations, the paper aims to bridge the gap between theory and practical applications, advancing the field of control engineering.

Keywords-Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy control; inverted pendulum on a cart; linear matrix inequality; decay rate; constraint on the output

I. INTRODUCTION

The IPOC system [1-3] stands as a captivating and challenging problem within the realm of control engineering, attracting the attention of researchers and engineers. This intricate system, characterized by its inherent instability, nonlinearity, and underactuation, has long been a crucible for testing and advancing control theories. The unique appeal of the IPOC system goes beyond theoretical fascination. It extends to practical applications that touch our daily lives, from the domain of self-balancing two-wheeled vehicles [4-5] to human balance modeling [6]. This paper explores the complexity of the IPOC system, emphasizing the core challenges stemming from its underactuated nature. As an underactuated system, controlling the IPOC presents challenges. Firstly, the system has a single input, the force applied to the cart, yet it must manage two output variables: the cart position and the pendulum angle. Secondly, this system is both nonlinear and unstable, making it susceptible to collapsing even under minimal disturbances. Consequently, the implementation of control methods becomes necessary to stabilize the pendulum.

Over the years, the research community has diligently explored numerous control methods to address the challenges of this system. Control strategies like Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID), Sliding Mode Control (SMC), Linear

Quadratic Regulator (LQR), and Fuzzy Logic Control (FLC) have been examined. Authors in [7, 8] utilized LQR and a PID controller, respectively, to stabilize the inverted pendulum. In [9], the authors used the IPOC as an object to test and compare the efficiency between SMC, Integral SMC and Terminal SMC. Besides those methods, FLC [10-12], has gained attention for its ability to handle the system's nonlinearity and ensure pendulum stability. While several studies have acknowledged FLC's potential in stabilizing the pendulum in the IPOC system, many of these studies have omitted practical considerations. The real-world environment often imposes limitations, including track boundaries and stabilization time. This brings us to the core of the current research. Acknowledging the merits of FLC, the untapped potential lies in adapting this method to consider real-world conditions. This paper introduces an approach using the T-S fuzzy control [13-15] to the control design of the IPOC. The objective is to combine the strengths of T-S fuzzy control with an awareness of external constraints, such as track limits and stabilization time, in order to create a control system that not only guarantees stability, but also respects the boundaries of practical application. Authors in [16] elaborated the establishment and substantiation of stability using Lyapunov's theorem. This work is primarily concerned with achieving stability for the inverted pendulum while disregarding external factors such as track limits and stabilization time. The aim is to

align theoretical insights with extended considerations. Therefore, the primary contributions of this paper include:

- Pendulum stabilization control design based on the T-S fuzzy model.
- Design of the controller with additional conditions through the LMI form.
- Result comparison and evaluation of the theorems both before and after the inclusion of additional conditions.

In this paper, the IPOC model will be introduced, stability theories both with and without the consideration of these conditions will be present, simulation results for validation and comparative analysis will be shown, and a comprehensive conclusion will be offered.

II. MODELING

The IPOC system is illustrated in the Figure 1. It includes a cart with mass denoted as m_0 and a pendulum with mass denoted as m_1 . The rotation angle of the pendulum from the Y-axis is represented as ϕ and the connecting rod has a length denoted as l . The force that moves the cart is expressed as u , and the acceleration due to gravity is represented by g . The travel distance of the cart is denoted as x_d and the coordinates of the pendulum are denoted as (\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}) with $\tilde{x} = x_d + l \sin \phi$, $\tilde{y} = l \cos \phi$.

Fig. 1 Inverted pendulum on a cart.

Assuming that the mass of the connecting rod is negligible, the Lagrange equation can be obtained as:

$$L = E_K - E_P$$

$$= \frac{1}{2}(m_0 + m_1)\dot{x}_d^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_1l^2\dot{\phi}^2 + m_1l\dot{x}_d\dot{\phi}\cos\phi - m_1gl\cos\phi \quad (1)$$

where the system's kinetic energy and potential energy are denoted as E_K and E_P , respectively. Using the Euler-Lagrange equations:

$$\frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{\delta L}{\delta \dot{x}_d}\right) - \frac{\delta L}{\delta x_d} = u$$

$$\frac{d}{dt}\left(\frac{\delta L}{\delta \dot{\phi}}\right) - \frac{\delta L}{\delta \phi} = 0 \quad (2)$$

the dynamics equations are derived:

$$\begin{cases} (m_0 + m_1)\ddot{x}_d + m_1l\ddot{\phi}\cos\phi - m_1l\dot{\phi}^2\sin\phi = u \\ l\ddot{\phi} + \ddot{x}_d\cos\phi - g\sin\phi = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

After applying specific transformations, the cart position and pendulum angle dynamics are:

$$\begin{cases} \ddot{x}_d = \frac{-m_1g\sin\phi\cos\phi + m_1l\dot{\phi}^2\sin\phi + u}{m_0 + m_1\sin^2\phi} \\ \ddot{\phi} = \frac{(m_0 + m_1)g\sin\phi - m_1l\dot{\phi}^2\sin\phi\cos\phi - u\cos\phi}{l(m_0 + m_1\sin^2\phi)} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

III. CONTROL DESIGN

A. The Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy Model

The T-S fuzzy model depicts a nonlinear system through its division into subsystems. Each subsystem is described using a local linear input-output relation through an IF-THEN rule. The overall system is derived by synthesizing the linear system models as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^r n_i(s(t))(A_i x(t) + B_i u(t)) \\ y(t) = \sum_{i=1}^r n_i(s(t))C_i x(t) \end{cases} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r \quad (5)$$

where the system's state vector is denoted as $x(t)$, the input vector is represented as $u(t)$, the output vector is described by $y(t)$, A_i , B_i , C_i are subsystem matrices, r is the number of rules, and $n_i(s(t))$ represents the membership functions, which, with their convex sum property, are defined as:

$$n_i(s(t)) = \frac{w_i(s(t))}{\sum_{i=1}^r w_i(s(t))}$$

$$\begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^r w_i(s(t)) > 0 \\ w_i(s(t)) \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, r \quad (6)$$

where $s = [s_1 \ s_2 \ \dots \ s_p]$ is a premise variables vector, p is the number of premise variables such that $r = 2^p$, and $w_i(s(t))$ are calculated by:

$$w_{i0} = \frac{s_{i\max} - s_i}{s_{i\max} - s_{i\min}}, \quad w_{i1} = 1 - w_{i0}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \quad (7)$$

Applying to the IPOC system, the premise variables are defined as:

$$s_1 = \frac{1}{m_0 + m_1 \sin^2 \phi}, \quad s_2 = \cos \phi$$

$$s_3 = \frac{\sin \phi}{\phi}, \quad s_4 = \dot{\phi} \sin \phi \quad (8)$$

The system's state equation takes the following form:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \tag{9}$$

where:

$$x = [x_d \quad \dot{x}_d \quad \phi \quad \dot{\phi}]$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -m_1 g s_1 s_2 s_3 & m_1 l s_1 s_3 s_4 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(m_0 + m_1) g s_1 s_2}{l} & -m_1 s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ s_1 \\ 0 \\ \frac{-s_1 s_2}{l} \end{bmatrix}$$

B. LMI-based Control Design

Upon constructing the T-S fuzzy model, the Parallel Distributed Compensation (PDC) [17] is structured to calculate the control signal $u(t)$. Each subsystem has a control rule corresponding to its T-S model. The fuzzy controller is designed using the identical fuzzy set as the premise part of the fuzzy model. With K_i being the feedback gain of the i^{th} subsystem, the overall PDC can be obtained as:

$$u(t) = -\sum_{i=1}^r n_i(s(t)) K_i x(t) \tag{10}$$

The PDC is derived through theorems in the form of linear matrix inequality. Some abbreviations used in the LMI context are: I is the identity matrix, $Q > 0$, $\alpha > 0$, $\lambda > 0$, $Z = Q^{-1}$, $G_i = K_i Z$. To design a controller with the aim of stabilizing the system, the following theorems should be held:

1) Theorem 1 [16]: Stability Conditions

The fuzzy system (5) achieves globally asymptotically stability when there is a common positive definite matrix Z such that:

$$\begin{cases} -ZA_i^T - A_i Z + G_i^T B_i^T + B_i G_i > 0 \\ -ZA_i^T - A_i Z - ZA_j^T - A_j Z \\ +G_j^T B_i^T + B_i G_j + G_i^T B_j^T + B_j G_i \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

Proof:

A Lyapunov function $V(x(t)) = x^T(t) Q x(t)$ is chosen. For the system (5) to achieve global asymptotic stability, the following condition must be satisfied:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x(t)) &< 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow \dot{x}^T(t) Q x(t) + x^T(t) Q \dot{x}(t) &< 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow (A_i - B_i K_j)^T Q + Q (A_i - B_i K_j) &< 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} -(A_i - B_i K_i)^T Q - Q (A_i - B_i K_i) > 0 \\ \frac{(A_i - B_i K_j)^T + (A_j - B_j K_i)^T}{2} Q - \\ Q \frac{(A_i - B_i K_j) + (A_j - B_j K_i)}{2} \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{12}$$

Multiplying on both sides of (12) with Z results in:

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} -ZA_i^T - A_i Z + G_i^T B_i^T + B_i G_i > 0 \\ -ZA_i^T - A_i Z - ZA_j^T - A_j Z \\ +G_j^T B_i^T + B_i G_j + G_i^T B_j^T + B_j G_i \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

This concludes the proof.

2) Theorem 2: Stability Conditions, Decay Rate, and Constraint on the Output

Regarding the IPOC system, stabilizing the inverted pendulum in an upright position is insufficient. Practical considerations, like constraining the cart position or stabilization time of the pendulum, come into play. Therefore, theorem 2 will be introduced to account for these additional conditions.

- Stability conditions:

$$\begin{cases} -ZA_i^T - A_i Z + G_i^T B_i^T + B_i G_i > 0 \\ -ZA_i^T - A_i Z - ZA_j^T - A_j Z \\ +G_j^T B_i^T + B_i G_j + G_i^T B_j^T + B_j G_i \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{13}$$

- Decay rate: The response's speed is related to decay rate. Maximize α subject to:

$$\begin{cases} -ZA_i^T - A_i Z + G_i^T B_i^T + B_i G_i - 2\alpha Z > 0 \\ -ZA_i^T - A_i Z - ZA_j^T - A_j Z \\ +G_j^T B_i^T + B_i G_j + G_i^T B_j^T + B_j G_i - 4\alpha Z \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

Proof:

We chose a Lyapunov function as $V(x(t)) = x^T(t) Q x(t)$.

From the condition that $\dot{V}(x(t)) \leq -2\alpha V(x(t))$, this is equivalent to:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}^T(t) (A_i - B_i K_j)^T Q x(t) + x^T(t) Q (A_i - B_i K_j) x(t) \\ + 2\alpha x^T(t) Q x(t) \leq 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow (A_i - B_i K_j)^T Q + Q (A_i - B_i K_j) + 2\alpha Q \leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Following stability conditions in theorem 1, it is inferred:

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} -A_i^T Q - Q A_i + K_i^T B_i^T Q + Q B_i K_i - 2\alpha Q > 0 \\ -A_i^T Q - Q A_i - A_j^T Q - Q A_j + K_j^T B_i^T Q + Q B_j K_j \\ + K_i^T B_j^T Q + Q B_j K_i - 4\alpha Q \geq 0 \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

Multiplying Z on both sides of (15), then (14) is obtained:

$$\begin{cases} -ZA_i^T - A_iZ + G_i^T B_i^T + B_i G_i - 2\alpha Z > 0 \\ -ZA_i^T - A_iZ - ZA_j^T - A_jZ \\ +G_j^T B_j^T + B_j G_j + G_i^T B_j^T + B_j G_i - 4\alpha Z \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

- Constraint on the output: With the assumption of knowing the initial condition $x(0)$, the constraint $\|y(t)\|_2 \leq \lambda$ is held if these LMIs are satisfied:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & x(0)^T \\ x(0) & Z \end{bmatrix} \geq 0 \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} Z & ZC_i^T \\ C_i Z & \lambda^2 I \end{bmatrix} \geq 0 \tag{17}$$

Proof: Following [17]. A Lyapunov function is chosen as $V(x(t)) = x^T(t)Qx(t)$ and assuming that:

$$x^T(0)Qx(0) \leq 1. \tag{18}$$

From $\|y(t)\|_2 \leq \lambda$, it can be inferred that:

$$\begin{aligned} y^T(t)y(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t)C_i^T C_j x(t) \leq \lambda^2 \\ \Leftrightarrow \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t)C_i^T C_j x(t) &\leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

Since $x^T(t)Z^{-1}x(t) < x^T(0)Z^{-1}x(0) \leq 1 \forall t > 0$, the above equation holds if:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\lambda^2} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t)C_i^T C_j x(t) &\leq x^T(t)Z^{-1}x(t) \\ \Leftrightarrow \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^2} C_i^T C_j - Z^{-1} \right) x(t) &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

From the left side of the above equation:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^2} C_i^T C_j + \frac{1}{\lambda^2} C_j^T C_i - 2Z^{-1} \right) x(t) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t) \times \\ &\left[\frac{1}{\lambda^2} (C_i^T C_i + C_j^T C_j) - \frac{1}{\lambda^2} (C_i^T - C_j^T)(C_i - C_j) - 2Z^{-1} \right] x(t) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^r n_i(s(t))n_j(s(t))x^T(t) \times \left[\frac{1}{\lambda^2} (C_i^T C_i + C_j^T C_j) - 2Z^{-1} \right] x(t) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^r n_i(s(t))x^T(t) \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^2} C_i^T C_i - Z^{-1} \right) x(t) \end{aligned}$$

So, $\|y(t)\|_2 \leq \lambda$ holds if:

$$\frac{1}{\lambda^2} C_i^T C_i - Z^{-1} \leq 0 \tag{19}$$

Multiplying Z on both sides of (19):

$$\frac{1}{\lambda^2} ZC_i^T C_i Z - Z \leq 0 \tag{20}$$

Using the Schur complement procedure for (18) and (20), LMI conditions (16) and (17) are derived.

By employing theorem 1 to the IPOC system, stability is achieved. Even though the inverted pendulum is maintained in a vertical position, the dynamics of the system requires additional conditions due to practical limitations. The length of the cart track is being limited and the stability duration should be kept relatively short. Consequently, theorem 2 is more applicable into this system. To validate the effectiveness of both theorems as well as demonstrate the superior performance of theorem 2 compared to theorem 1, the simulation results will be presented in the following section.

IV. SIMULATION

The parameters for simulation are chosen as: $m_0 = 1.5$ kg, $m_1 = 0.3$ kg, $l = 0.3$ m, $g = 0.3$ m/s². The system's initial conditions are: $x(0) = [x_{d0} \ \dot{x}_{d0} \ \phi_0 \ \dot{\phi}_0]$, $x_{d0} = 0$, $\dot{x}_{d0} = 0$, $\phi_0 = \frac{\pi}{6}$ (rad), $\dot{\phi}_0 = 0$. The boundaries are $-\frac{\pi}{3} \leq \phi \leq \frac{\pi}{3}$ (rad), $-6 \leq \dot{\phi} \leq 6$ (rad/s). Additionally, the parameters in theorem 2 are given as $a = 0.9$, $\lambda = 7$. The calculated values of $s_{i \max}$ and $s_{i \min}$ are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. PREMISE VARIABLES VALUES

i	$s_{i \max}$	$s_{i \min}$
1	0.6667	0.5797
2	1	0.5
3	1	0.827
4	5.1962	-5.1962

The simulation results when employing both theorems are shown in Figures 2-6. The blue line depicts the system's states and control signal for theorem 1, whereas the red line represents those for theorem 2. Figures 2 and 3 illustrate cart position and cart velocity, respectively. The pendulum angle is described in Figure 4 and the pendulum angle velocity is shown in Figure 5. Figure 6 presents the control signal.

Fig. 2 Cart position.

In Figure 2, the position of the cart under theorem 1 and theorem 2 are compared and the difference is evident. The results show that theorem 2 achieves a significantly faster cart position stabilization time (approximately 2 s) compared to theorem 1 (about 30 s). It's worth noting that the cart position response curve for theorem 2 reaches a maximum value of approximately 0.6 m, whereas under theorem 1, this maximum value is as high as 1.7 m. This confirms the earlier assertion that theorem 2 provides results that align more closely with real mechanical constraints.

Fig. 3 Cart velocity.

Fig. 4 Pendulum angle.

Fig. 5 Pendulum angle velocity.

Similar to the cart position results, the pendulum angle also exhibits faster stabilization when applying theorem 2 compared to theorem 1 (2.5 s compared to 5 s), as shown in Figure 4.

Once again, these results further bolster the points mentioned earlier. In Figures 3 and 5, respectively, the speed of the cart and the angular speed of the inverted pendulum are shown for both theorems. Although there are differences between the results, these state variables remain within the prescribed limits. Figure 6 illustrates the force acting on the cart, reflecting a subjective judgment aimed at finely regulating the system's dynamics. This translates to a higher energy exchange. Consequently, the force applied to the cart in theorem 2 is greater than that in theorem 1.

Fig. 6 Control signal.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the control design through two theorems and their application to the inverted pendulum on a cart system. Simulation results have been presented after introducing the theorems and proving their effectiveness, highlighting the superiority of theorem 2 over theorem 1. This research represents a significant step towards applying these theorems to control design for experimental systems, potentially contributing to advancements in control engineering.

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An Ensemble Method for EEG-based Texture Discrimination during Open Eyes Active Touch

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ABSTRACT

Touch sensation is a key modality that allows humans to understand and interact with their environment. More often than not, touch sensation depends on vision to accumulate and validate the received information. The ability to distinguish between materials and surfaces through active touch consists of a complex of neurophysiological operations. To unveil the functionality of these operations, neuroimaging and neurophysiological research tools are employed, with electroencephalography being the most used. In this paper, we attempt to distinguish between brain states when touching different natural textures (smooth, rough, and liquid). Recordings were obtained with a commercially available EEG wearable device. Time and frequency-based features were extracted, transformed with PCA decomposition, and an ensemble classifier combining Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, and Neural Network was utilized. High accuracy scores of 79.64% for the four-class problem and 89.34% for the three-class problem (Null-Rough-Water) were accordingly achieved. Thus, the methodology's robustness indicates its ability to classify different brain states under haptic stimuli.

Keywords-haptic; active touch; electroencephalogram; classification; multisensory; machine learning; PCA; ensemble method

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the basic human mechanisms for perceiving and exploring the surrounding world is the sense of touch. It is one of the earliest developed senses and plays a crucial role in daily tasks like object manipulation and action performance. Sensory loss of touch could lead to someone being unable to feel pain or temperature, missing the sense of presence, not being able to effortlessly move [1], and/or experience other atypical implications.

Acquiring information about the surroundings through touch requires physical contact and interaction between the surface of an object and the human skin, most commonly through the fingertips due to their high sensitivity. This contact results in the mechanical stimulation of the skin where mechanoreceptors transduce a nerve signal which is transferred through the peripheral nervous system pathways to the central nervous system and the brain. There, high order somatosensory areas, mainly the postcentral gyrus [2], are involved in the process of interpreting the signal. Information regarding the physical and geometric properties of the material, object, or surface being touched can be extracted. Such properties can be about the object's shape and size, the material substance and texture, hardness and elasticity, roughness, or temperature [2, 3]. This information analysis in the brain, integrated with proprioceptive, kinesthetic, cutaneous and thermal characteristics is called haptic perception. Haptic perception includes active and passive touch (tactile). The former occurs when human body parts are willingly used for exploration by moving against the surroundings while the latter is performed when outside agencies interact with static parts of the human skin [4]. Neural operations and perceptual differences between those two forms are still under investigation with numerous studies substantiating diversities in performance, in the activated brain area discrimination and in the neural response patterns involved [5-8]. Haptic perception is not limited to a fundamental ability of distinguishing different material properties. It is a subjective experience [9, 10] that has the capacity to create mental apprehension of the surroundings, both discriminatively and affectively [11]. Visual, auditory, and memory aspect incorporation complementarily contributes to constituting a multimodal system [9] that impacts the emotional, social and cognitive human apprehension [13-15]. Understanding the way human senses work, and more particularly how haptic perception functions has become a growing research topic over the recent years [13]. The importance and reasoning behind decoding haptic modality are driven by the numerous applications spotted in human psychology and physiology. Starting from the medical field with applications such as limb rehabilitation and assistive haptic robotics [16], neurophysiological disorder treatment [17], therapeutic interventions on tactile deficits in humans with mental disorders (anorexia nervosa) [18], and stroke rehabilitation [19], haptic perception understanding extends to most parts of human activity. The Industrial field makes use of the affective sensations through touch for manufacturing commercial products [20] like fabrics or clothes. Technological novelties, interface and application design utilize the knowledge on haptic perception to develop haptic interfaces

[21], tactile displays, interactive media devices [22], and affective computing [23].

Non-invasive neuroimaging and neurophysiological methods including functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Electroencephalogram (EEG) enable researchers to examine the brain's response to touch stimuli. Especially the EEG portability, ease of use, low cost, and high temporal resolution, have generated novel experimental scenarios related to haptic sensation research. Corresponding studies implement analysis techniques such as Power Spectral Density [6, 24], event-related potentials [25], and somatosensory evoked potential [26-28]. In addition, advancements in machine learning technologies are combined with EEG analysis techniques to conclude in the classification of different brain states under haptic stimuli. These studies investigate discriminative touch and touch imagery [29, 30], roughness recognition classification [6, 31, 32], and tactile pleasantness in response to different textures or touch types [12, 33, 34]. Most studies examine active touch after eliminating the visual stimuli since it may have a major impact in haptic perception [35]. However, tactile perception in combination with visual stimuli has also been explored. Authors in [36] proposed a classification scheme for object shape recognition from EEG signals acquired with both tactile and visual stimuli. They used electrodes located on the frontal somato-sensory and occipital region that are responsible for the cognitive processing and the employment of Power Spectral Density and Mu-desynchronization.

In this research, we seek to address the multisensory nature of haptic perception and distinguish brain responses when touching different materials. Specifically, we propose a methodology for the discrimination of different natural material textures during active touch and constant visual contact through EEG signal classification. Multisensory stimuli can improve the classification accuracy more than conventional, single-sensory input [37]. Commonly, publications do not employ multiple machine learning algorithms for the classification procedure investigating active touch [6]. We designed an experimental protocol for EEG acquisition and preprocessing, then performed feature extraction, implemented Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and employed multiple classification algorithms for the EEG signal categorization under different haptic stimuli. Ultimately, we suggest an ensemble classification method that exceeds in performance every classifier tested.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the stages of the proposed methodology. First, the experimental protocol for obtaining and preprocessing the EEG recordings is set out. Then, the procedure for extracting the features used for the classification of each active touch condition is explained, along with the dimensionality reduction of the feature matrix. Finally, the algorithms and the ensemble method used for performing the classification of the active touch states are described. Figure 1 represents a diagram of this experiment's entire methodology.

A. Dataset

The experimental procedure was held in a clinical, quiet and controlled environment. For this experiment, participants were asked to comfortably sit in a chair and a researcher explained them the procedure. They were given time to familiarize with the device and were instructed to relax during the experiment. Then, their right hand (dominant hand as validated with Edinburg Handedness Inventory [38]) was positioned in a fixed ergonomic arm support. The texture materials were visible while the participants were asked to use their right hand fingertips to softly rub each texture for one minute, in a circular, clockwise manner, without applying pressure on any material. The participants were asked to keep having visual contact with the material throughout the 1-minute active touch recording. In order to minimize the variance in movements and pressure applied, participants arms were fixed on the arm support with a rubber band and calibrated on their respective relative height horizontal to the surface position. An experienced researcher was always supervising the procedure.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed methodology.

The protocol in brief steps:

1. 1-minute eyes-open resting-state recording.
2. 1-minute recording during active texture rubbing smooth surface.
3. 1-minute rest.
4. 1-minute recording during active texture rubbing rough surface.
5. 1-minute rest.
6. 1-minute recording during active texture touching liquid surface.

In total, 12 participants took part in the experiment, 7 males and 5 females. The participant age was between 25-27 years old. Every participant was right-handed with no history of neurological or psychiatric disorders. Detailed information about the procedure was given to every participant prior to the experiment by an experienced researcher. Written consent forms were obtained, ensuring that there was no concern regarding the experimental protocol and that their EEG recordings along with their private data could be used for publication purposes. The natural textures used in this study were: two materials of different roughness levels (smooth and rough) and liquid. For the smooth material, a satin polished stainless steel was employed with $R_a < 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ (Roughness average). For the rough material, a piece of a 120 Grit sandpaper was used (estimated $R_a = 1.32 \mu\text{m}$). For the liquid surface, room temperature water (10^{-3} Pa.s.) in a shallow container was utilized. The Emotiv EPOC Flex wearable device was hired for the EEG data recording. This device is equipped with 32 gel Ag/AgCl sensors and a flexible cap. It is a portable headset with a rechargeable lithium battery and each electrode frequency response is 0.16-43 Hz, while the device sampling rate is 1024 Hz. The electrode placement was in accordance with the extended 10–20 International Reference System and 32 electrodes were positioned (Cz, Fz, Fp1, F7, F3, Fc1, C3, Fc5, T9, T7, Tp9, Cp5, Cp1, P3, P7, O1, PZ, OZ, O2, P8, P4, Cp2, Cp6, Tp10, T8, Fp10, Fc6, C4, Fc2, F4, F8, Fp2). Also 2 electrodes were placed on the ear lobes, namely A1 and A2. CMS and DRL electrodes were P3 and P4, respectively. The recording quality was constantly being ensured in real-time, by using the native EmotivBCI interface, which provides real-time information about electrode connectivity and signal quality. An experienced researcher continuously ensured that the electrode connection was at the best state according to the EmotivBCI interface, by reapplying gel on the electrodes if needed, so as every electrode impedance value would constantly be below the designated value ($<20 \text{ k}\Omega$). The recordings were streamed to a PC via a wireless connection to be saved and later processed. Figure 2 illustrates the materials used and the experimental procedure.

B. Data Preprocessing and Feature Extraction

The EEG recordings were digitally rereferenced to the average of A1, A2 electrodes which were placed at the left and right ear lobe, respectively. Recordings were downsampled from 1024 to 128 Hz during the wireless transmission stage. Furthermore, a 4th order Butterworth high-pass filter at 0.4 Hz

was applied. No low pass filter was set since the Emotiv EPOC Flex firmware automatically applies a double notch filter at 50 Hz and 60 Hz to remove interference from the electrical power supply. Also, Emotiv Flex has a built-in low-pass filter of 45 Hz [39]. The filter affects frequencies down to about 45 Hz, so the manufacturer specifies 43 Hz as the upper usable frequency limit where the spectral response is perfectly flat [40]. Next, artifacts of electrode movement were manually removed from visual inspection, in the EEGLAB MATLAB environment. No electrodes were removed from any of the EEG recordings, only time segments.

Fig. 2. The experimental protocol and the materials used: smooth, rough, liquid.

Subsequently, epoching of the EEG signals was performed. Signals were segmented into 1 s epochs with 0.5 s overlap. Epochs of 2 and 5 s were also extracted and the duration of 1 s was chosen based on the accuracy results. Afterwards, time and frequency domain metrics were extracted from each epoch to form the classification dataset. The time domain metrics were: Mean, Variance, Range, Median, Interquartile Range, 30% Percentiles. Frequency domain features were the Spectrum Power Density of each frequency band, for each epoch, calculated with the Power Spectral Density Welch method. The frequency bands were defined as [41]:

- Alpha: 8-12 Hz

- Beta: 12-25 Hz
- Theta: 4-8 Hz
- Delta: 1-4 Hz
- Gamma: 25-43 Hz

In total, 352 features were extracted (6 time domain and 5 spectral domain features for each of the 32 electrodes).

C. Dimensionality Reduction

PCA is a widely used method for dimensionality reduction in high-dimensional datasets. For a p -dimensional dataset, PCA analysis creates a p -dimensional vector of weights $w_{(k)} = (w_1, \dots, w_p)_{(k)}$ projecting each row vector $x_{(i)}$ to a new principal component score vector $t_{k(i)} = x_{(i)} * w_{(k)}$ for $i = 1, \dots, n$ and $k = 1, \dots, p$ where n is the number of the individual recordings on the data [42]. To achieve the highest variance, the first principal component is computed so that the sum of each point squared distance is maximized. Then, each other principal component is calculated in order to have the maximum sum of squared values while being perpendicular to all its previous principal components. After calculating the principal component transformation, one can perform dimensionality reduction to the dataset by removing the components with the least variance. Thus, projecting a dataset of p -dimensional data to a dataset of r -dimensional data where $r < p$. In this experiment, the feature vector was standardized before the PCA transformation was calculated and then the less important principal components, which accounted for less than 5% of the total variance, were discarded (95% variance threshold). This way, the initial dataset of 352 features was converted to a linear transformation of 75 features. Figure 3 represents the PCA dimensionality reduction procedure followed in this dataset. PCA is implemented for reducing the feature space of the datasets capitalized by the classification algorithms, to achieve faster computational time and higher accuracy.

Fig. 3. Visual representation of the PCA stages: Original dataset, standardized dataset, principal component variances, PCA decomposition.

D. Classification

In this section, the utilized classification algorithm are described, those being: Random Forest (RF), k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN), Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), C4.5 Decision Trees (DTs), Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA), and Support Vector Machines (SVMs). The ensemble method is also presented. For each classification case, accuracy (ACC), sensitivity (SENS), and specificity (SPEC) scores were calculated. Equations (1)-(3) represent how ACC, SENS, and SPEC are computed for a binary problem. TP stands for True Positive, TN for True Negative, FP for False Positive, and FN for False Negative, respectively.

$$ACC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (1)$$

$$SENS = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

$$SPEC = \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \quad (3)$$

To calculate these metrics in a multiclass problem, we averaged their scores in one versus all binary problems.

The four classes in the classification were:

1. Resting state or Null (N)
2. Rough (R)
3. Smooth (S)
4. Water (W)

These classes were combined in 4 classification problems:

1. N-R-S-W
2. N-S-W
3. N-R-W
4. N-R-S

The accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity scores of every classification problem were obtained by using the 10-fold validation method. Every classification algorithm and the ensemble method were employed in the Weka platform [43] while the hyperparameter optimization for each algorithm took place in Python, using the `skopt.gp_minimize` routine [44]. The Standard Deviation (SD) of the accuracy for each algorithm has been calculated after performing the classification routine 10 times.

E. C4.5 Decision Tree

DT algorithms are some of the most widely used methods for inductive inference [45]. C4.5 is an algorithm, first introduced by Ross Quinlan [46] that generates a DT robust to noisy data and capable of learning disjunctive expressions. The idea behind DT classification is to develop an if-else formula that can correctly determine an unknown instances class. The algorithm for producing a DT is quite simple. Beginning from the original training set, the information gain of each attribute - if split- is calculated. Then the attribute with the higher information gain value is selected and the tree is divided into subtrees based on this selected attribute. This procedure is

repeated for each subtree until every element in the subset belongs to the same class or there are no more attributes to be selected. It should be noted that an attribute cannot be selected again as a partition attribute in the same subtree. To avoid overfitting, pruning techniques can be used. In this experiment, pruning by information gain in which a node is no longer expanded to a subtree and becomes a leaf based on a confidence factor was put to work. Reduced error pruning was employed as well, where a node is pruned if the resulting tree still has the same accuracy score as the unpruned version.

F. Random Forest

RF algorithm is an ensemble classifier [47, 57] and one of the most common techniques for classifying EEG data [48, 49]. This classifier involves multiple DTs, each of which uses a different subset of features as classification criteria and a different bootstrapped dataset (sampling with replacement) created from the original one as the training set. Then, each DT votes for each observation in the test set and the observation gets classified based on the average probability voting. Different weights can be given to each tree. This method employs the bagging idea to reduce the generalization error and improve classification accuracy. In this experiment, each tree was given the same weight. Moreover, no pruning of the created DTs was performed. The number of estimators to be used was obtained by the `skopt.gp_minimize` optimization pipeline in Python, which employs Bayesian Optimization utilizing Gaussian Processes, and found to be 110.

G. K-Nearest Neighbors

KNN algorithm classifies an instance of the test set by calculating its distance (Euclidean, Manhattan, etc.) from every instance in the training set while considering the majority class of the k-nearest ones [50]. In this experiment, k was set to 5 and the computed distance was Euclidean. The value of k was chosen after testing different k values from 1 to 10 and the one that produced the highest accuracy result was chosen.

H. Multi-Layer Perceptron

MLP is a commonly used feed forward Neural Network. An MLP consists of: an input layer with as many neurons as the dataset attributes, an output layer with as many neurons as the dataset classes, and one or more hidden layers. Each neuron receives multiple real-valued inputs and produces one real-valued output, determined by the activation function, usually being the sigmoid function. The `gp_minimize` pipeline was applied to calculate the learning rate which was found to be 0.32. Regarding the number of neurons and hidden layers, there are several methodologies for defining the optimal ones [51-53]. In this experiment, we used a trial-and-error technique to define the hidden layer size. Different hidden layer setups were implemented and finally it was decided to use one hidden layer with 39 neurons (the average of input plus output number of neurons).

I. Linear Discriminant Analysis

LDA is a dimensionality reduction technique that is also utilized as a classification method in many EEG classification problems [54] LDA aims to reduce the feature vector dimensionality by creating a new dimension that maximizes the

variance between each class. First the between-class scatter is calculated using equation 4.

$$S_b = \sum_{i=1}^g N_i (\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})(\bar{x}_i - \bar{x})^T \quad (4)$$

The within-class scatter is produced by calculating the covariance matrix of each class

$$cov_j = (x_j - \mu_j)(x_j - \mu_j)^T \quad (5)$$

and then by computing their average:

$$S_w = \sum_j p_j \times (cov_j) \quad (6)$$

The a priori probability of the class j , is p_j .

The LDA optimizing criterion is maximizing the S_b/S_w ratio. The transformed space axes are defined by maximizing this criterion. Once the LDA is completed, each data point of the test set is classified based on the smallest Euclidean distance from the class centers.

J. Support Vector Machines

A Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a machine learning algorithm that can solve binary classification problems. They have been widely encountered in biomedical applications and in EEG analysis [55, 58-60]. The SVM basic principle is to map the features to a high-dimensional feature space and locate an optimal separating hyperplane that maximizes the width of the gap between the two classes. To perform non-linear classification, an SVM can utilize the kernel method [56]. For multiclass classification such as the 4- or 3-class classification problems in this experiment, the classification problem is broken down into multiple two-class classification problems, in a one versus one approach. Additionally, in this experiment, the kernel function was a radial basis function. The kernel function selection was made after evaluating the performance results of every kernel function, namely linear, polynomial, radial basis, and sigmoid in the LibSVM implementation on the Weka platform [43].

K. The Ensemble Method

The proposed ensemble method is an average probability voting system consisting of the 3 best performing classification algorithms in this dataset: MLP, RF, and SVM. Initially, each classification algorithm is trained with the training set. For each instance of the test set, every classifier calculates the probability estimations for each class. Then the classifiers "vote" by averaging their probability estimations. The assigned class is the one with the higher average probability.

To examine the ensemble method's usefulness and check whether the employment of multiple classifiers with different architecture enhanced classification performance by eliminating the errors made by the classifiers, we conducted Mathews correlation of errors between the individual classifiers and between the Ensemble Method with each classifier. To do so, the individual results of the classification were extracted while an array of 0 and 1 was created for each classifier, with 0 representing a classification error and 1 representing a correctly classified instance.

III. RESULTS

In the first classification problem, where all 4 experimental classes were used (Null, Rough, Smooth, Water), the voting system achieved a level of ACC of 79.64% (SENS=77.30%, SPEC=92.40%) outperforming the other classifiers and achieving the lowest SD of 2.19. MLP was the second best with 77.06% ACC followed by SVM (ACC 76.50%) and RF (ACC 70.86%). Table I illustrates the results of the N-R-S-W classification problem.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE RESULTS FOR THE N-R-S-W CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM

Algorithm	ACC	SD	SENS	SPEC
Voting system	79.64%	2.19	77.30%	92.40%
RF	70.86%	2.32	70.80%	90.20%
DT	47.14%	2.83	47.10%	82.30%
KNN	64.90%	2.52	67.00%	89.00%
LDA	67.80%	2.35	67.80%	89.20%
SVM	76.50%	2.21	76.40%	92.10%
MLP	77.06%	2.33	77.00%	92.30%

In the second classification problem, where 3 experimental classes were considered (Null, Smooth, Water), the voting system achieved an ACC level of 87.67% (SENS=85.90%, SPEC=93%) outperforming all other classifiers while achieving the lowest SD (2). MLP was the second best with 84.70% ACC followed by SVM (ACC 84.50%) and LDA (81.10%). RF scored an ACC level of 79.30%. The rest of the classifiers achieved ACC lower than 72%. Table II shows the results of the N-S-W classification problem.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE RESULTS FOR THE N-S-W CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM

Algorithm	ACC	SD	SENS	SPEC
DT	55.64%	3.64	57.10%	78.50%
RF	79.30%	2.51	79.60%	89.80%
KNN	71.22%	2.94	72.20%	86.00%
MLP	84.70%	2.34	84.80%	92.40%
LDA	81.10%	2.39	81.10%	90.50%
SVM	84.50%	2.26	84.50%	92.20%
Voting system	87.67%	2.00	85.90%	93.00%

In the third classification problem, 3 experimental classes were used (Null, Rough, Water). The voting system achieved an ACC level of 89.34% (SENS=85.90%, SPEC=93%) outperforming all other classifiers and achieving the lowest SD of 1.42. MLP was the second best with 86.50% ACC followed by SVM (ACC 86.30%), RF (82.56%), and LDA (82.25%). KNN achieved an accuracy level of 74.31% while DT performed the lowest, with an ACC score of 60.1%. Table III shows the results of the N-R-W classification problem.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE RESULTS FOR THE N-R-W CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM

Algorithm	ACC	SD	SENS	SPEC
DT	60.10%	3.55	60.00%	80.00%
RF	82.56%	2.56	82.50%	91.20%
KNN	74.31%	3.37	77.10%	88.50%
MLP	86.50%	2.36	86.40%	92.00%
LDA	82.25%	2.22	82.10%	91.00%
SVM	86.30%	1.99	86.30%	92.10%
Voting system	89.34%	1.42	85.90%	93.00%

In the fourth classification problem, where three experimental classes were used (Null, Rough, Smooth), the voting system achieved an ACC level of 82.10% (SENS=79.80%, SPEC=89.9%) outperforming the other classifiers and achieving the lowest SD of 2.33. Nevertheless, it performed noticeably worse than in the other 3-class classification problems. SVM was the second best with 79.13% ACC followed by MLP (ACC 78.33%) and RF (75%). The other classifiers achieved accuracy lower than 72%. Table IV shows the scores of the N-R-S classification problem.

TABLE IV. PERFORMANCE RESULTS FOR THE N-R-S CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM

Algorithm	ACC	SD	SENS	SPEC
DT	54.27%	3.48	56.00%	78.00%
RF	75.00%	2.67	75.00%	87.40%
KNN	70.06%	3.27	71.40%	85.70%
MLP	78.33%	2.89	78.10%	89.00%
LDA	70.62%	2.74	70.60%	85.30%
SVM	79.13%	2.62	79.20%	89.60%
Voting system	82.10%	2.33	79.80%	89.90%

Figure 4 exhibits the comparison between the ACC scores of each classifier in the four classification problems. It can be noticed that, overall, the N-R-S-W problem achieved the lowest ACC scores, while the N-R-W problem achieved the highest ones. Concerning the 3-class problems, the performance in the N-R-S problem, was noticeably lower than in the others. Figure 5 represents the overall ACC, SENS and SPEC scores comparison among all the algorithms across all problems.

Fig. 4. All classification algorithm accuracy comparison.

To evaluate individual classifier contribution, the correlation of each classifier's error in-between them, and the correlation of each classifier's error with the ensemble method should be investigated. The Matthews correlation results are depicted in Table V. Low correlation between individual classifiers, along with higher correlation between the Ensemble Method and each classifier indicate that the classifiers do not misclassify the same instances and there is a benefit on using a combination of these classifiers (also based on the comparison of the performance results). Finally, to further investigate the performance of the proposed methodology for each classification problem, we calculated the Area Under Curve (ROC AUC) of each class versus the rest (OvR), along with the Precision Recall Curve (PRC) Area. The results are reported in Table VI.

TABLE V. CORRELATION OF ERRORS BETWEEN CLASSIFIERS

Mathews correlation	SVM	MLP	RF	Voting system
SVM	---	0.33	0.4	0.75
MLP	0.33	---	0.3	0.564
RF	0.4	0.3	---	0.59

TABLE VI. AREA UNDER ROC AND PRC FOR EVERY CLASSIFICATION PROBLEM

Problem Class	N-S-R-W		N-R-W		N-S-W		N-R-S	
	ROC	PRC	ROC	PRC	ROC	PRC	ROC	PRC
1	0.974	0.951	0.972	0.962	0.975	0.963	0.984	0.973
2	0.933	0.812	0.972	0.952	---	---	0.917	0.823
3	0.914	0.813	---	---	0.964	0.934	0.909	0.852
4	0.967	0.914	0.969	0.935	0.966	0.934	---	---
Average	0.947	0.872	0.971	0.95	0.968	0.944	0.937	0.883

IV. DISCUSSION

In this paper, a robust methodology for classifying EEG signals during active touch on different textures was implemented. The study consisted of four stages: experimental procedure, data acquisition, signal preprocessing, and classification. At the first stage, the participants were asked to touch actively 3 different materials while maintaining minimum arm movement and their brain function was recorded using an EEG wearable device. At the second stage, the EEG signal was preprocessed and different features were extracted which were later transformed using a PCA decomposition. Finally, this reformed feature dataset was used to train an ensemble classifier. The ensemble classifier consisted of a voting system of 3 distinct classifiers (RF, MLP, SVM), each of them utilizing a different classification principle. Finally, the proposed methodology was tested on 4 different classification problems and proved to be very effective since high accurate results were achieved.

In previous preliminary work on the same dataset, we observed that utilizing both temporal and spectral feature characteristics provided better classification accuracy in comparison to employing only spectral features [61]. However, other studies have highlighted that non-linear feature characteristics such as entropy [32] and determinism may also be useful for classifying active touch states considering the non-linear nature of brain signals and haptic perception entanglement. Table VII presents a list of previous works related to haptic task classification and the used methodology.

This research suggests that by using PCA feature reduction, the training and testing times are reduced while higher overall ACC is achieved. The voting system time performance was improved by 95% when PCA was applied. Particularly, the voting system's training time was 42 s in the 4-class classification problem. When training the voting system with the original non PCA-reduced dataset, the training time was 887 s. Similar time performance improvements were achieved in every classification problem. This is due to the fact that choosing the number of neurons in the neural network depends on the number of the dataset features. Therefore, by reducing the feature matrix from 353 to 75 features, both memory and time demands were decreased.

TABLE VII. COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS WORKS

Reference	Year	Experimental protocol	Methodology	Classification problem	Results		
					ACC	SENS	SPEC
[32]	2020	Dynamic passive touch, rotating surface, roughness.	Features: Recurrence rate, determinism, LDA.	Rough, smooth, semi-rough.	93%	-	-
[31]	2021	Active touch, roughness, synthesized textured surfaces.	Deep learning CNN	Rough, smooth, semi-rough.	70%		
[6]	2019	Active touch, roughness, synthesized textured surfaces, different rubbing speeds (slow, medium, fast).	PSD, Features: Alpha and beta bands, time, SVM.	Flat, medium rough.	90.2%	83.3%	
[30]	2021	Active touch, haptic imagery, textures, finger slide	Features: Alpha and beta bands, common spatial pattern, LDA, event-related spectral perturbation analysis.	4 textures real touch, 4 textures imagery touch.	68% (real touch) 7.55% (imagery touch)		
[10]	2019	Affective tactile stimulation, 4 different fabrics, self assessment, arousal, valence	PSD, KNN.	Arousal, valence.	74.24%		
Proposed	2023	Active touch, fixed hand position, circular motion rubbing, 3 surfaces	Spectral and time features, PCA, ensemble method.	N-R-S-W	79.64%	77.30%	92.4%
				N-S-W	87.67%	85.9%	93%
				N-R-W	89.34%	85.90%	93%
				N-S-R	82.1%	79.8%	89.9%

Fig. 5. ACC, SENS, SPEC scores of all algorithms across every problem.

Regarding how the PCA transformation can influence the classification performance, we can observe that the voting system ACC is significantly increased in all classification problems. The comparison of the ACC scores with and without PCA-transformed data is presented in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII. VOTING SYSTEM ACC RESULTS WITH AND WITHOUT PCA-TRANSFORMED DATASET

Classification problem	With PCA	Without PCA
N-R-S-W	79.64%	52.41%
N-S-W	87.67%	69.72%
N-R-W	89.34%	68.89%
N-R-S	82.10%	63.47%

The 3-class problem classifications were tested along with the 4-class problem classifications in order to examine whether their accuracy differences were significant. As expected, the 4-class problem classification problems achieved lower ACC scores. However, it can be observed that the classification ACC of the N-R-S problem (82.1%) is inferior to the N-R-W and N-S-W counterparts (87.67% and 89.34%, respectively), indicating a possible variation in the brain reception mechanisms triggered during the contact with a liquid surface. The utilized voting system proved to be effective since its classification performance was consistently higher than that of individually employed SVM, RF, and MLP. Specifically, in all classification problems, the voting system achieved 0.5% to 3.5% higher ACC while maintaining lower SD scores. To further validate that the ensemble method provides better

performance in comparison to the other algorithms (especially SVM), we conducted independent sample T-tests between the ACC results of the SVM algorithm (10 runs) and the ensemble method (10-runs) for each classification problem. The performance difference for all the problems was statistically significant, with every p -value <0.001 .

The scope of this research was to classify the different active touch states while performing a predetermined hand movement and having visual contact with the texture. Other studies have tried to identify distinct brain behavior under different haptic stimuli [34, 62, 63]. However, no specific protocol has been established regarding the experimental procedure during the signal acquisition. The elaborate nature of haptic perception and the complex functionality of cutaneous and kinesthetic mechanoreceptors have allowed researchers to employ a wide range of approaches and tools. In the majority of the other studies, the experimental protocol about hand movement is extensively controlled. For example, authors in [32] had the participants place their hands in a completely motionless state, while authors in [30] allowed only a finger slide. Furthermore, almost every study regarding haptic perception has the participants keeping their eyes closed during the experiment. Depending on the scope of research there is a focus on the exploration control, attempting to isolate the stimuli. According to [4], the distinction between active and passive experimental procedures can be questioned on whether the active approaches are truly active. Our study allowed an adequate degree of freedom on the finger motion while restraining any hand and arm movement along with maintaining visual contact with the material. By doing so, we attempt to simulate a natural approach of a human exploring a surface in a quest to identify its characteristics. Moreover, contrary to other research approaches that use only specific brain regions or feature selection methods for keeping the dataset dimensionality low, we choose not to dismiss information of the perplexed neural connections but to perform, instead, the dimensionality reduction through a PCA decomposition process. We achieved an ACC score of 79.64% for a 4-class problem and an 89.34% for a 3-class problem in our classification between all subjects with all the electrodes available and not at a single-subject level classification. Thus,

direct comparison with other research cannot be performed, mainly because of the dissimilarities in the experimental protocol and the differences in the classification approach.

The brain mechanisms have the ability to get acquainted to a continuous stimulus. This may lead this classification routine to reduced performance if the participant is exposed to the stimuli for too long. Although this classification protocol was strict considering the time duration of the experiments, it should be examined whether there are significant changes in the EEG features exported right after the stimuli induction with the EEG features exported after the brain had already got familiar with the stimuli. We examined whether there was a performance drop when using tactile perception EEG signals that have been recorded after a certain duration of activity, in two ways. First, we split the feature dataset in two subsets. The first one containing the former 30 time windows of each recording (30×1 s epochs). The latter containing the last 30 time windows. We performed the 4-class classification pipeline 10 times. The ACC score of the first group of epochs at average was 78.75% and the ACC of the second was 80.18%. Independent sample T-test was carried out and the difference in performance was not found to be statistically important, meaning that this classification problem is not time dependent. However, this should be further validated by obtaining longer EEG recordings. Also, an independent T-test was employed between the features of each participant at every state (resting state, rough, smooth, water). Every test with p -value less than 0.05 was classified as 1 (statistically significant differences) and every test with p -value bigger than 0.05 was classified as 0. For every participant, the percentage of features that presented statistically important differences at each state was calculated. It was observed that: (1) even in the resting state recordings, 27.8% of the features had significant changes without an obvious cause. (2) Regarding the tactile perception recordings, 21-26.4% of the features had significant changes. Table IX represents the percentages of features that presented statistically important changes between the 2 states along with the difference percentage between the resting state and the active state. In total, more than 75% of the features did not present statistically important changes, which indicates that this model is not strongly time-dependent.

TABLE IX. PERCENTAGE OF FEATURES WITH STATISTICAL IMPORTANT CHANGES, FOR EVERY PARTICIPANT, BETWEEN THE FIRST 30 S AND THE LAST 30 S OF A RECORDING

Participant	% Statistical important changes				% Difference of resting state with tactile perception
	Rest	Rough	Smooth	Water	
1	0.193	0.196	0.161	0.187	0.011
2	0.235	0.068	0.215	0.400	0.007
3	0.264	0.207	0.130	0.241	0.071
4	0.298	0.463	0.420	0.295	-0.094
5	0.420	0.153	0.406	0.326	0.125
6	0.156	0.215	0.326	0.244	-0.106
7	0.468	0.153	0.252	0.190	0.269
8	0.082	0.491	0.073	0.204	-0.174
9	0.156	0.318	0.497	0.093	-0.146
10	0.389	0.159	0.181	0.230	0.198
11	0.409	0.119	0.230	0.366	0.170
12	0.264	0.059	0.176	0.392	0.054
Average	0.278	0.217	0.256	0.264	0.032

The limitations of this methodology should be addressed. To begin with, increasing the EEG recording should produce more accurate and generalizable results. Also, analyzing the neurophysiological brain activity during the experiment could lead to a better understanding of the interaction between specific brain regions and possible result in a more elaborate feature extraction procedure. In addition, considering the degrees of freedom in the finger movement, the classification procedure may be affected by the individual's way of interaction. Conscious or unconscious decisions made by individuals regarding speed, strength, and muscle movement may affect the joint and muscle mechanoreceptor activity. Finally, the non-randomized experimental protocol of this experiment can be considered a limitation, because of the uncertainty of whether the order of the trials may enhance or reduce the classification accuracy due to mental factors such as fatigue. However, randomizing the trial order could lead to other limitations such as the non-repeatability of the experiment or, in the case of the water trial, preceding the smooth or rough trial, moisture remaining on the hand may affect the EEG signal. Thus, we considered the non-randomized protocol as our best option.

Nevertheless, the above limitations regarding the motor movement and the cognitive brain function during the active touch are to be leveraged in our future work. We intend to dissociate visual-to-haptic combination by exploring the differences of eyes-open and eyes-closed haptic exploration. Additionally, the next stage of this research will aim to explore the imagery aspects of active touch when using virtual reality and head mounted displays. Future work could indicate whether visual and cognitive touch imagery could be distinguished without actual touching within virtual reality environments. Moreover, the communication patterns between brain regions during haptic stimulus are to be explored in that sense.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a technique for categorizing EEG signals during active contact, obtaining notable accuracy in a variety of categorization settings is proposed. To achieve high accuracies of 79.64% for the N-R-S-W problem, 87.67% for the N-S-W problem, 89.34% for the N-R-W problem, and 82.1% for the N-R-S problem, we strategically integrated SVM, MLP, and RF algorithms through an ensemble method. We used PCA to reduce the number of features, which not only sped up computation but also improved the precision and robustness of our classifications. Importantly, our results confirmed the time-independence of the categorization approach, demonstrating its endurance over extended time. This robustness highlights our method potential for more extensive applications when combined with our ensemble methodology. These findings can have a wide range of applications. Our study has possible implications in prosthetics, robotics, and communication restoration in addition to advancing our understanding of EEG-based tactile discrimination, especially given its proven stability and precision.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that the current research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Wear and Hardness Characterization of Hot Forged Tungsten Carbide reinforced Aluminium 6061 Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

The current study intends to examine how forging under hot conditions affects wear characteristics of tungsten carbide (WC) particles reinforced aluminum alloy 6061 composites. The reduction ratios of 20%, 40%, and 60% were employed during forging, and the percentages of reinforcement used were 0, 2, 4, and 6 (weight fractions). The investigation clearly showed that the forged composites had a substantially lower wear rate than the unforged composites. It was discovered that the wear behavior of the composite improved due to the higher content of WC particles present in the matrix. Enhanced wear rate was observed as the weight and sliding distance increased.

Keywords-wear; hardness; hot forging; aluminum alloy; composites; tungsten carbide

I. INTRODUCTION

Scientists and engineers are constantly looking for lightweight materials, particularly for uses in quickly expanding industries like aerospace and automotive. Alloys made of aluminum and magnesium are good choices for lightweight applications. However, it is crucial to keep in mind that aluminum lacks the stiffness and strength that are crucial for many applications, thus there is a need to increase its qualities by employing appropriate reinforcement [1]. Composites made from aluminum alloys have poor formability as well as issues with particle breakage and matrix-reinforcement decohesion [2]. Additionally, reports indicate that the typical manufacturing techniques adopted for Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) frequently produce reduced ductility due to the usage of highly brittle reinforcements and

uneven microstructure, which lead to issues with porosity and agglomeration [3]. Using appropriate forming procedures to produce improved characteristics is a useful strategy for addressing the issues related to composites [4]. Authors in [5] reported on the performance of composite materials made of aluminum that were rolled or extruded. Only a few studies have looked at how forging operations affect the mechanical properties and wear rate of aluminum alloy-based composites [6]. Potential candidates for racing purposes have been thought of as forged pistons made of aluminum/SiC composites [7]. There are other reports available on various drive-train parts, particularly the connecting rod [8]. This study's main goal is to investigate how hot forging operations affect the wear characteristics of Al-WC composite materials made up of various amounts of WC reinforcement and forging conditions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study aims to evaluate the impact of hot forging and reinforcing WC particles on the wear performance of composites made of 6061 aluminum alloy. Table I presents the composition of the alloy used in the present study. When creating composite samples, WC particles with sizes ranging from 10 to 25 μm were used as reinforcement.

TABLE I. COMPOSITION OF ALUMINUM ALLOY 6061

Al	Mg	Si	Cr	Mn	Ti	Cu	Fe	Zn
95.8 – 98.6	0.8 – 1.2	0.4 – 0.8	0.04 – 0.4	0.15	0.015	0.15 – 0.4	0.7	0.25

WC particle reinforced aluminum alloy composites of various compositions were created utilizing the stir casting method of liquid metallurgy. The calculated weight percent of WC particles was 2, 4, and 6. The aluminum alloy was melted in an electric furnace and the desired amount of 400 °C-preheated WC particles were added while it was still liquid. After allowing the castings enough time to cool, they were machined to the correct size and shape required for the forging process. The as-cast specimens were heated to 450 °C and hot forged at several reduction ratios of 20%, 40%, and 60%. The samples were examined for their wear behavior under dry (unlubricated) circumstances as per ASTM G99 standards by using a pin-on-disc tribometer. The counter facing disc on which the specimen was made to slide was EN 32 steel. The disc had 68 HR_C hardness. The selected loads ranged from 30 N to 50 N in steps of 10 N. The disc speed was 1000 rpm. In the test, sliding distances ranging from 1000 m to 3000 m in stages of 1000 m were used. After the tests, a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) was used to examine the specimens' worn surfaces. In addition to the wear tests, the specimens underwent hardness tests using a Brinell hardness tester. Ten different readings were collected for each specimen at various positions on the samples.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figures 1-4 show the wear rate of the specimens in relation to the reinforcement content for different sliding distances and loads (30, 40, and 50 N) and forging conditions (20%, 40%, and 60% forging) at a constant speed of 1000 rpm. The wear rate of unforged composites under different sliding distances and loads are shown with reference to the weight % of WC particles in Figure 1. Additionally, it was discovered that regardless of the sliding distances and reinforcing content, the wear rate rises as the load increases. Figure 2 which depicts the wear behavior with respect to the content of WC for various sliding distances for a 20% forged composite under various loads. In all situations, a similar wear performance is seen in the 40% forged condition, despite the fact that the wear resistance continues to increase, as illustrated in Figure 3. The outcome showed that the composite materials' wear resistance differs significantly after forging at a higher percentage than 40%. The wear rate rises as the applied load rises for 60% forging conditions. The graphs shown in Figure 4 show the behavior of wear rate of 60% forged composites under various load conditions. When evaluated at 30, 40, and 50 N loads in contrast to the unreinforced alloy, it could be observed that the

unforged composite samples containing 6% reinforcement particles revealed a lower wear by 29.17%, 26.92%, and 21.43%, respectively. Similarly, the reduction in the wear rate for the forged composites with 6% reinforcement compared to the unreinforced and unforged samples was 44.41%, 40.82%, and 36.45%, respectively, when examined at 30, 40, and 50.

Fig. 1. Effect of WC on wear rate of unforged composites at constant load of (a) 30 N, (b) 40 N, (c) 50 N, under various sliding distances.

Fig. 2. Effect of WC on wear rate of of 20% forged composites at constant load of (a) 30 N, (b) 40 N, (c) 50 N, under various sliding distances.

The observations show that the reinforcing particles significantly contribute to the composites' better wear resistance through a decrease in wear rate. This observation is unmistakably caused by the composite specimens' release of WC particles onto the mating surface during the tests, thereby providing wear resistance. The WC particles are sheared during the sliding contact wear process, and those layers adhere to the

metal surfaces and align in the sliding direction to form a thin film sandwiched between the mating surfaces. Additionally, under low load conditions, the rigid film of WC has very little plastic deformation potential and may endure stress without breaking.

Fig. 3. Effect of WC on wear rate of of 40% forged composites at constant load of (a) 30 N, (b) 40 N, (c) 50 N, under various sliding distances.

This observation may be the result of an increase in temperature caused due to enhanced friction between the contact surfaces. It should be noted that higher temperatures

cause significant surface plastic deformation. Subsurface delamination followed by asperity fracture and fragmentation were the results of this. Therefore, it follows that the reinforcing WC particles help the composites' composites have better wear resistance. During the first rubbing action, the reinforcing WC particles serve as a load-bearing material and extremely effectively reduce wear. Additionally, the reinforcing WC particulates function as inhibitors preventing plastic deformation, and also adhering of the aluminum alloy to the wear disc surface [9].

The study also included hardness tests with the intention of ascertaining the influence of the WC reinforcement. The results for the forged and unforge samples are shown in Table II. Hard WC particles were added to the composites to increase their hardness, which can be linked to the composites' enhanced resistance to wear. Additionally, the composite material's porosity dramatically decreases, increasing its resistance to crack propagation. The results clearly show that the matrix and reinforcement have a strong link even after forging, which has a significant impact on wear behavior, improves the ability of the matrix to transfer load to the reinforcement, and increases the wear behavior of the composite. Such observations are in line with those made in [10].

The analysis revealed that the specimen exposed to the 40% forging condition, offered the composites the most excellent wear resistance, which can be ascribed to the forging process because the composites' strength and hardness were greatly improved. It is clear that the layer of oxides that forms on the surface causes the adhesive metal wear to decrease at higher temperatures. The model proposed in [9] can be used to describe the several phases that contribute to the creation of an oxide layer which is resistant to wear.

Fig. 4. Effect of WC on wear rate of of 60% forged composites at constant load of (a) 30 N, (b) 40 N, (c) 50 N, under various sliding distances.

TABLE II. HARDNESS RESULTS (BHN) OF TESTED SAMPLES

Reinforcement % (WC)	Unforged composites	Forged composites
0	72	78
2	81	89
4	88	97
6	96	104

The concentrated huge wear product particles disintegrate into smaller particles, go through oxidation process backed by sintering process, and then cover the entire wear surface. Therefore, it follows that at high temperatures, the rate of wear decreases due to the production of an oxide layer, which causes the change from an adhesive to an oxidative wear. Figure 5 displays the SEM images of the worn surfaces of the unreinforced alloy and the composite with 6% WC at test condition of 50 N load and 2000 m sliding distance. Figure parts 5(a)-(c) pertain to worn surfaces of unreinforced alloy, while 5(d)-(f) pertain to composite samples containing 6% WC reinforcement. Figure parts 5(a),(d) relate to worn samples tested under 20% forging conditions, while 5(b),(e) pertain to those with 40% forging conditions, and 5(c),(f) are for 60% forging conditions.

Abrasion, delamination, and oxidation are the three main types of wear mechanisms. The main type of wear is abrasion, which is seen in all the specimens as scratches, grooves, and other debris. The wear asperities on the steel counter-face or hard particles between the pin and the disc that cut into the samples and wear it by removing minute pieces are the distinguishing features of abrasive wear [11]. It is immediately obvious that deeper grooves are indicated by a greater extent of impregnation by harsh counter-face asperities. The asperities of the steel disc deform the asperities of the sample's soft surface, and as a result, shear deformation causes microcracks to occur close to the subsurface area of the pin's softer material.

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs showing worn out surfaces of unreinforced alloy (a, b, and c) and composite samples with 6% WC (d, e, and f) at load of 50N and sliding distance of 2000m under 20% forging condition (a and d), 40% forging condition (b and e) and 60% forging condition (c and f).

Later, the pieces separate from the pin surface and become wear debris. Delamination wear is the term used to describe this tendency [12]. The formation of a fracture was seen around the hard particles during the sliding activity between the pin and the disc, and delamination clearly was visible in the SEM microstructures when the pin was made to slide on the steel disc.

IV. DISCUSSION

The current study presents very interesting and significant results which are likely to have relevance to the practical world. The literature shows that not much work has been conducted regarding the influence of metal forming operations on wear behavior of composites. However, the results obtained in the present study are in agreement with the results obtained by several other studies [2, 5, 8, 10]. The novelty of the present work lies in the fact that hot forging as a process can significantly reduce the wear rate of composites thereby contributing to enhanced wear resistance. Several components that are prone to wear in the practical world such as bearings, couplings, pulleys, gears, shafts, etc., can be made this way, thus acquiring an extended life cycle.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper deals with the effect of hot forging and WC particles on the wear behavior of composites. The results are of great significance since the effect of forging and reinforcement is found to be very profound in improving the wear behavior. It

was found that the wear behavior of the composites improved due to the presence of higher content of WC particles in the matrix. It was observed that the wear behavior of the composites subjected to forging operation was better than that of the unforged counterpart. Further, the wear rate of the reinforced composites was observed to improve with the addition of reinforcing WC particles. Also, the wear rate was indirectly proportional to the content of reinforcement in the composites. This observation was found to be true for all the sliding distances taken into consideration. It was also evident that the wear rate had a direct relation with the load applied up to 40% reduction, which subsequently decreased due to the acute plastic deformation of the composite samples.

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ABSTRACT

Communication system and internet dominance in our society, has made image security a matter of paramount concern. Cryptography involves encrypting data to protect information exchange between senders and receivers, establishing a foundation for secure communication. The Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is an exceptional algorithm that plays a pivotal role in this area because of its ability to consistently transform plain data into cipher data using the same encryption key. This algorithm engages intricate encryption techniques, harnessing a variety of algorithms and transformations to ensure robust data security. This study introduces an image encryption technique to comprehensively address security requirements. The proposed approach uses encryption to provide high reliability and security, effectively protecting sensitive media from unauthorized access. The sender's file is divided into multiple pieces to maximize confidentiality, using an advanced algorithm. Upon proper decryption, these pieces seamlessly reconstruct the original file. The suggested technique enables customers to securely keep information on cloud storage, addressing concerns about possible leakage, damage or corruption. By integrating cloud storage and digital signatures, this method ensures protection and reliability for sensitive information.

Keywords-cloud computing; cryptography; encryption; decryption; AES algorithm; digital signature; openSSL

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's interconnected world, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive data is crucial. Whether related to business, personal affairs or other important information, there is an ongoing need to protect data from unauthorized access and misuse. Cryptography plays a key role in achieving secure communication, providing a framework to safeguard data even when transmitted over public networks where not all viewers may be trusted. As a multifaceted field, cryptography is dedicated to techniques for concealing and authenticating information stored and shared digitally, such as in cloud environments. Its core function is to transform data in a way that only approved individuals with the proper credentials can comprehend its true meaning. In an environment where data

breaches and cyber incidents have become common, cryptography provides fundamental security by validating users and shielding information from improper access or alteration. Through encryption and related methods, it aims to uphold privacy, integrity and safe transfer of sensitive data online and in the cloud. As technologies continue to connect the world in new ways, responsible use of cryptography remains important for responsible data stewardship [1]. Fundamentally, cryptography consists of two steps: data concealment through encryption and data restoration for authorized users through decryption. By converting data into an incomprehensible format, encryption protects it against unauthorized access. This procedure is reversed during decryption, enabling descriptors to effectively access and utilize protected data [2-4]. Segmentation is a technique used to improve the security of

digital assets. Files are split up into smaller, encrypted components and then securely rejoined. This fortifies the barriers against unauthorized access to or alteration of private information. To verify file ownership and integrity, more methods can incorporate authentication levels. By using private/public key pairs, one may verify there was no transmission manipulation and avoid impersonation. Mismatches caused by incorrect keys indicate potential problems that should be looked into.

Cryptography is also useful in fields such as online commerce, communications, healthcare data, and government/military applications [5]. It underlies technologies that provide privacy, security, and identification, such as passwords, digital signatures, and distributed systems. As threats change with new capabilities, so does cryptography via novel research, underlining its continued importance for digital interactions and information safety in an interconnected society. Responsible implementation helps maintain security standards and data stewardship practices in many spheres of contemporary life.

A. Problem Statement

Image security, especially in cloud-based storage and communication systems, is a major problem. Malicious attackers are always present, posing a persistent danger to critical visual data security and integrity. To overcome this challenge, the scientific community has turned to cryptography for an answer. Among the different encryption methods, the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is notable for its ability to reliably convert plain pictures into encrypted ones while utilizing the same encryption key. To guarantee comprehensive data protection, AES utilizes advanced encryption techniques, varied algorithms, and transformations. However, there is still a need to improve and optimize AES for even greater degrees of picture privacy.

B. Motivation

The motivation behind this study stems from the pursuit of unparalleled image security (with the AES algorithm significantly contributing to this goal accomplishment). By intelligently fragmenting sender images and embracing cutting-edge cloud-based techniques, this study aims to maximize image confidentiality, minimize vulnerability to attacks, and empower users to safely store their data in the cloud without fear of the latter being compromised.

C. Contribution

This study makes several significant contributions to the field of cloud image security and cryptography:

1. It presents an optimized AES algorithm specifically addressing to image safety, ensuring high reliability and protection against malicious attacks.
2. It employs a novel fragmentation technique to enhance image confidentiality, making the former more sealed against breaches.
3. It introduces a cloud-based image security method, allowing safe data storage in the cloud, and mitigating risks of intended data damage or corruption.

4. It integrates digital signatures via OpenSSL to certify tight security and reliable verification of the recipient's identities.

II. BACKGROUND

Cryptographic algorithms play an essential role in protecting data in cloud computing environments due to the significant benefits they bring to cloud computing [6-7]. Cryptographic algorithms come in various forms, each designed to address specific security needs and challenges. Broadly, they can be categorized into two main types:

- Symmetric key encryption: One secret key is utilized for both encryption and decryption in symmetric key encryption. AES and DES are two well-known examples of symmetric key algorithms. The algorithms are highly efficient and suitable for safeguarding data at rest within the cloud.
- Asymmetric key encryption: Two keys are used in asymmetric key encryption, sometimes referred to as public-key encryption: a public key and a private key. It is only possible to decrypt data encrypted with the public key with the matching private key, and vice versa. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) and Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA) are two popular asymmetric key algorithms that are useful for safe key exchange and data protection while in transit.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies and research efforts have been carried out to explore and enhance the performance and safety of cryptographic algorithms in cloud computing environments. Several studies have investigated security in cloud computing and Internet of Things (IoT) [1, 8-12]. In [13], a proposal was presented to improve the AES algorithm to better address emerging privacy threats in the cloud. The results showed that the suggested method had increased encryption speed, reduced power consumption, better load balancing, and upgraded trust and resource management. Additional investigation suggested a lightweight encryption approach to accelerate the encryption and decryption procedures [14]. In [15], an improved Blowfish algorithm was combined with an elliptic curve-based algorithm to achieve effective data confidentiality and integrity in cloud computing. This hybrid approach enhanced security and performance, while ensuring data integrity through digital signatures. Most of the research on secure data transmission in a cloud storage environment has been focused on symmetric and asymmetric encryption techniques. Data privacy is usually assured through the use of tools like RSA and AES while other methods such as packet parsing and rule generation protect against passive data attacks [16]. Another study [17] compared hybrid AES and RSA techniques to the Blowfish/Paillier-based protocol's efficiency. The new hybrid protocol aims at boosting cloud storage by ensuring data integrity, reducing ciphertext size, improving computation time. In [18], a cloud RSA encryption system was presented, using distinct evaluation and private keys. This approach allowed third parties to perform operations on encrypted data, using the evaluation key, while the private key was only known to the data owner.

In [19], an in-depth performance assessment of various symmetric cryptographic algorithms in a cloud computing environment was carried out, including DES, 3DES, Blowfish, Twofish, RC2, RC5, RC6, and AES. The evaluation considered algorithm structure, encryption/decryption times, throughput, and memory consumption. Some of research in fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) has proposed a unique and efficient FHE scheme that can be homomorphically verified, to address the challenge of efficiently managing noise and making FHE more practical for real-world applications, especially in cloud environments [20-21]. These works attempted to overcome the difficulty of efficiently handling noise, making FHE more applicable to real-world applications, especially in cloud environments. Hybrid encryption techniques were presented in [22] in order to improve data privacy on cloud servers. costumers have the option to select their preferable encryption methods like Eclipse IDA, DSA, RSA, AES, and

Blowfish, instead of relying on encryption provided by third parties. For the purpose of maximizing the security of cloud data, the current study also experimented a number of cryptographic techniques and developed a hybrid encryption architecture. In [23], the authors introduced homomorphic encryption and offered a structure for Mobile Multi-Cloud computing (MMC) analysis and evaluation. Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) was utilized in their study [24] to reinforce cloud computing security and enable servers to match different customers' expectations. The principle goal of this work was to analyze the response times in relation to the size of the public key, and to facilitate the FHE method. These outcomes demonstrate the necessity to use more measures to decrease emerging risks, strengthen cloud data security, and increase the efficiency, reliability, and utilization of cryptographic algorithms.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF LITERATURE REVIEW

Reference	Key Contributions	Algorithms Used	Notable Outcomes
Current Research	Modified AES for better speed, reduced power, and better load balancing	Enhanced AES	Improved security, reduced resource usage, lower latency
[15]	Combined enhanced Blowfish with an elliptic curve-based algorithm	Blowfish, Elliptic Curve	Improved security and performance, ensured data integrity
[16]	Comparison of symmetric and asymmetric methods; using RSA and AES	RSA, AES	Mitigated passive attacks, ensured data confidentiality
[17]	Hybrid protocol based on Blowfish and Paillier; compared with AES and RSA	Blowfish, Paillier, AES, RSA	Reduced calculation time and ciphertext size, enhanced security and integrity
[18]	Cloud (RSA) with distinct evaluation and private keys	RSA	Allowed third-party operations on encrypted data, maintained data ownership
[19]	Evaluated DES, 3DES, Blowfish, Twofish, RC2, RC5, RC6, AES	DES, 3DES, Blowfish, Twofish, RC2, RC5, RC6, AES	Considered algorithm structure, encryption/decryption times, throughput, memory consumption
[20-21]	Novel symmetrically verifiable FHE scheme	Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE)	Made FHE more practical for cloud applications
[22]	Hybrid encryption approaches, consumer choice in encryption methods	Blowfish, RSA, AES, Eclipse IDA, DSA	Optimized cloud data protection, various cryptographic techniques explored
[23]	Introduced homomorphic encryption for data security	Homomorphic Encryption	Evaluated homomorphic encryption in mobile cloud computing
[24]	Applied FHE to enable server operations for client requests	Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE)	Reduced FHE algorithm complexity, assessed response times

IV. EXISTING METHODS AND PROPOSED MODEL

A. Digital Signature

It is highly important to make a difference between digital signatures from other types of signatures, such scanned physical signatures, email headers, and letterheads, for them having various aims. Digital signatures simplifies the procedure of authenticating communications sent by customers and confirming their identity

B. One-Way Hash Functions

One-way hash algorithms are utilized to generate digital authorizations for photographs. These programs transform each message—graphics comprised—into a fixed-length message digest, typically 128 bits in length. It is usual practice in the business to use hash algorithms to securely encrypt communications. Hash algorithms are very reliable, hard to reverse engineer, and provide distinct values for every image. MD2, MD4, and MD5 are known examples of hash algorithms.

C. Message Digest Security

In order to protect against manipulation or unauthorized access, the message digest is encrypted using a public key approach such as RSA. This demonstrates that the message integrity is maintained and that any modifications are simple to detect.

D. AES Algorithm

AES is a symmetric key cryptographic technique, which means that it uses the same cryptographic key for both encryption and decryption. This type of encryption confirms that data can be safely encrypted and decrypted, using the same key. AES relies on block cipher encryption where data are encrypted by substituting, transforming, and permuting. The data are divided into states, each consisting of 128-bit elements organized in a matrix format with rows and columns serving as its keys. Each element within the matrix is called a cell. AES offers various security levels through its different variants, each employing a different number of rounds. The key sizes for AES encryption are in increments of 128, 192, and 256 bits. However, regardless of the variant, the block size and the round

key size remain fixed at 128 bits. AES excels in the following four key tasks:

1. Encryption: AES encrypts data using a symmetric key, ensuring its confidentiality during transmission or storage.
2. Decryption: The same AES key is used for decryption, allowing authorized recipients to recover the original data.
3. Substitution: AES uses substitution operations to transform the data during encryption.
4. Permutation: AES uses permutation operations to further enhance encrypted data security and complexity.

Digital signatures and AES are crucial components in signifying data authenticity, integrity, and confidentiality. Digital signatures verify the sender's identity and message integrity, while AES safeguards the data itself, providing secure communication and storage capabilities. AES performs the following four fundamental operations:

- Sub Bytes Operation: Sub Bytes Operation: Replaces An 8-bit S-box determines the unique byte for each byte in the state.
- Shift Rows Operation: Shifts the i^{th} row in the state matrix to the left by a specified number of bits.
- Mix Columns Operation: The state matrix columns are subjected to this process, employing a transformation matrix that independently alters each column.
- Add Round Key Operation: This operation is a critical step during the encrypting procedure. It involves adding a round key element to each state matrix column generated through XOR operations.

The AES encryption process begins with the plaintext encoded, followed by a series of rounds that employ the Add Round Key operation. These rounds continue until the final round, which consists of only three operations, and omits the Mix Columns step. Round keys, distinct from the cipher key used for data encryption, are required for the Add Round Key operation, and are generated through the key expansion process. Importantly, the encryption process must be reversed, except for the Add Round Key method to decrypt the data. This reversibility makes decryption the inverse of encryption.

Encryption changes a straightforward sentence into a corresponding ciphertext image by generating a particular key. Moreover, the decryption process is just the opposite of it. Thus, it can be explained as changing the same key that was used to encrypt it, returning the ciphertext image to its original legible format. Moreover, the decryption process is just the opposite of it. Thus, it can be explained as changing the same key that was used to encrypt it, returning the ciphertext image to its original legible format. Because it makes sure that only those with permission may access the information, this process is essential to data security. Image splitting and merging is another method for protecting IT data by cutting the picture into many little parts and then gathering them again. This method is very good at hindering the disclosure or modification of private information.

E. Project Flow

The first step is dissecting an original image into its component elements. Next, each component is encrypted utilizing an AES encryption algorithm by using its private key. Adhering this particular plan renders exchanging photos with other people secure, simple, and generative. To affirm their integrity within transmission and cloud server storage, these photos are further double encrypted. When the pictures come to be viewed, authorized receivers may regenerate its original state using their private keys. This method depends completely on digital signatures, which are composed of both private and public keys that are generated from images. This digital signature is produced by the sender of the image. After then, the images' receiver confirms its authenticity by checking this signature. This two-pronged method impressively promotes the genuineness and authenticity of image sharing.

Fig. 1. Encryption flow.

Fig. 2. Decryption flow.

F. Problem Description

Enhancing image security has been a preferred ability for cloud storage solutions. The outcome of one such endeavor was the creation of the program "Secure Image Preservation in Cloud Environments: Leveraging AES and Digital Signatures." This project's primary objective is to safeguard image data against alteration, illegal access, and even forgeries. reinforcement of the authenticity, creditability, and integrity of image data stored in the cloud is its main:

- Each of the image files (I_1, I_2) that compensate image data (I) is a digital copy of a different picture.
- Cloud Storage: Image files are preserved remotely and may be accessed by using programming application interfaces and protocols.
- Digital images are encrypted utilizing AES. Using a symmetric key K , the encryption and decryption processes are implemented simultaneously.
- Digital signature: The authenticity and integrity of image files are guaranteed by digital signatures. When making a digital signature, a personal key ($PrKey$) must be owned along with a public key ($PubKey$) to affirm that the signature is authentic.
- Encryption Process: The image data I is encrypted, using the AES algorithm and the encryption key K . The encrypted image data is represented as $Enc(I, K)$.
- Image data I employs the AES for encryption and key K . $Enc(I, K)$ is the encoding for the encrypted image data. The notation $Dec(Enc(I, K), K)$ is used to denote the decrypted image data.
- Digital Signature Generation: A digital signature is created for each image file I_i using the $PrKey$. An example of a constructed signature would be $Sign(I_i, PrKey)$.
- Digital Signature Verification: The validity and integrity of an image file I_i are verified by comparing its digital signature $Sign(I_i, PrKey)$ with the corresponding public key $PubKey$.

In summary, this project aims to secure image data stored in cloud storage systems by employing AES encryption for confidentiality and digital signatures for integrity and validity verification. This comprehensive approach ensures the protection and trustworthiness of image files in cloud-based storage environments.

V. ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system "Image Security Enhancement on Cloud Storage Using AES Algorithm and Digital Signature" offers a robust solution for addressing the security challenges associated with image data stored in cloud environments. This analysis delves into the key aspects of the system and evaluates its effectiveness in achieving the stated objectives.

- Enhanced confidentiality: One of the primary goals of the system is to improve data confidentiality. Utilizing the AES algorithm, image data are encrypted with a symmetric key before being stored in the cloud. This encryption ensures that even with unauthorized access, the data remain unreadable without the corresponding decryption key. AES, known for its strength and reliability, provides a solid foundation to maintain sensitive data privacy.
- Integrity assurance: Digital codes are utilized by the technology to verify that image files are correct. A digital signature made with a private key is tied to each picture file. This signature is like an encryption mark; it proves that the picture was not changed while being sent or stored. The

public key that goes with the signing is used to make sure that the picture has not been changed. This thorough integrity check is very important to make sure that the saved pictures can be trusted.

- Verification and grant of permission. Digital signatures make sure that only people who are allowed to and have access to the secret key can make accurate signatures. This plan makes things safer by proving who the writer is and letting people who are allowed to use digital signatures do so.
- Data recovery and reconstruction: If access is granted, the technology can turn encrypted pictures back to the way they were before they were encrypted. The AES decoding method lets people who have the right encryption key get to and get back picture data. This feature lets you get back lost info while keeping it safe.
- Cloud storage integration: The system works with cloud storage services without any problems thanks to APIs and standards. This link makes sure that protected pictures are saved safely in remote cloud storage, profiting from the cloud's ability to grow and be accessed from anywhere.
- The system's interface is easy for approved users to use and understand, so picture data can be changed while still being safe. This makes it easy to get to while still meeting protection needs. The AES encryption and recovery processes are designed to be as quick and easy as possible for the system.

Fig. 3. Original image.

Fig. 4. Split images.

Fig. 5. Encrypted images.

Fig. 6. Decrypted images.

Fig. 7. Merge Image (Original).

Fig. 8. Generate private key with OpenSSL.

Fig. 9. Generate the digital certificate with OpenSSL.

Fig. 10. Extract the public key from the certificate.

An essential aspect of the system's operation, shown in Figure 12, is the generation and validation of file digital signatures. When the outcome reads "success" after verifying a file's signature, it means the file is authentic and uncorrupted. Put simply, the file was not subject to any unauthorized

changes or manipulations while it was being stored or sent. To validate the dependability of the files stored on the system, this verification step is necessary. This part of the system checks all files for modifications and uses only the ones that are still valid

Fig. 11. Create a hash of the image.

Fig. 12. Verify with public key.

A. Performance Evaluation

The proposed method was evaluated on a Core i7 laptop with Windows 10 using parameters like Avalanche Test, Visual Assessment, Correlation and Statistical Analysis, Time Complexity, Execution Time, Image Histogram, and Image Entropy to compare its efficiency against traditional algorithms. Table I shows the basic measurements, and Tables II and III illustrate the results of the image entropy test and the differential cryptanalysis.

TABLE II. BASIC MEASUREMENTS

Original Image	Size	
	After Encryption	After Decryption
125 Kb	125 Kb	125 Kb
Encryption time		Decryption time
10 s		5 s

Surprisingly, after encryption, the picture file size stayed constant at 125 KB. This shows that the encryption mechanism used in the system does not considerably increase file size. It's advantageous because it makes it easier to store and send protected images. The file size stayed at 125 KB after decryption, the same as in the original picture. This result shows that the decryption process worked to get the picture back to its original size without missing any data or quality. It took 10 seconds to finish the encryption process, which is the same amount of time it took to change the original image into an encrypted version using the AES method. On the other hand, decryption was much faster; it only took 5 seconds to get the encrypted image back to how it was before it was encrypted. It follows that decryption is a faster process that may use fewer resources than encryption.

B. Overall Implications

The consistent file size before and after encryption and decryption is a positive outcome, as it certifies that the security measures do not introduce unnecessary file size overhead. The processing times for encryption and decryption are reasonable, with decryption being notably faster. This suggests that users

can efficiently access their original images with minimal delay after decryption. The system appears to strike a balance between safety and efficiency, offering users the benefit of secure image storage and transmission without significantly affecting file size or processing time. The measurement table indicates that the proposed system effectively maintains file size consistency and provides reasonable processing times for encryption and decryption operations, making it a practical solution for securing image data in cloud storage.

TABLE III. IMAGE ENTROPY TEST

No	Image	Dimensions	Entropy (ORG)	Entropy (ENC)
1	Baboon	128x128	7.2608	7.9891
		220x220	7.1662	7.9958
		256x256	7.2091	7.9973
2	Lena	128x128	7.4810	7.9885
		220x220	7.4618	7.9962
		256x256	7.4436	7.9970
3	Banda	256x256	7.5966	7.9969
		512x512	7.5217	7.9982
5	Peppers	256x256	7.5519	7.9970
		512x512	7.5555	7.9992

TABLE IV. DIFFERENTIAL CRYPTANALYSIS

Image	Size	NPCR	UACI
Baboon	256x256	99.5826	26.3210
Lena	256x256	99.5758	25.0544
Banda	256x256	99.6052	23.0526
Peppers	256x256	99.6231	31.1101

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Image security is significant in many different circumstances in our everyday life. Data guarding is critical, precisely when transferred over open networks like cloud services. Encryption techniques are strictly tested to improve the encryption procedure and display solid security. Moreover, the use of digital signatures enhances the privacy of encrypted images by giving permission to receivers to give credibility to the authenticity of the received data, so reinforcing the system's legitimacy. The present study proposes an image fragmentation and encryption system that combines the AES algorithm and digital signatures to safeguard cloud-stored images against malicious attacks. There is opportunity to improve the image security system by integrating sophisticated authentication procedures. Future research can focus on incorporating multifactor authentication mechanisms, like biometrics, smart cards, or single-use passwords, to improve the security of accessing and retrieving picture data from cloud storage. Furthermore, blockchain technology offers unique characteristics such as distribution, transparency, and tamper resistance, giving a new approach to image security in cloud contexts.

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Enhanced Skin Cancer Classification using Deep Learning and Nature-based Feature Optimization

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a skin cancer classification model that combines a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with a nature-inspired feature optimization algorithm. A custom dataset comprising both malignant and benign skin cancer microscopic illustrations is derived from the ISIC dataset of dermoscopic images. Several preprocessing steps are performed on the input pictures, such as histogram equalization, gamma correction, and white balance adjustment, to improve visibility, quality, and make color corrections. Deep feature extraction and pattern recognition are conducted on both enhanced and original dataset images using the pre-trained CNN model EfficientNetB0. As a result of fusing these features, the model can capture rich details from both dataset versions at the same time. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), a nature-inspired feature selection algorithm is applied to perform model optimization by keeping the most relevant features and discarding the unnecessary ones. The optimized feature vector is then used with various SVM classifier kernels for the skin cancer classification task. The maximum achieved accuracy of the proposed model exceeded 98% through CB-SVM while maintaining an excellent prediction speed and reduced training time.

Keywords-skin cancer; deep learning; CNN; Ant Colony Optimization (ACO); classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin cancer occurs in the upper skin layer, which contains squamous cells, basal cells, and melanocytes. Skin cancers that do not involve the melanocytes, like squamous cell and basal cell types, can often be successfully treated and not spread. However, malignant melanoma, another cancer type, is more dangerous if not detected early [1]. Early melanoma detection can help cure them, but it can be very difficult to treat them if they spread further into the skin and other body parts. Melanoma development occurs when melanocytes, the pigment-producing cells in the skin, undergo harmful changes. In addition to containing brown or black shades, it can also exhibit pink, red, or purple colors when there is no pigment present. Skin cancer diagnosis can be improved through a

variety of methods and computer systems such as the seven-point checklist and the ABCD rule [2]. Early melanoma detection is crucial, but it remains challenging even for specialists [3]. Detecting skin cancer early is essential for a high chance of recovery, but it can be costly due to the resemblance of skin lesions. Dermatologists often use expensive dermoscopes for close examination. The effectiveness of dermoscopy is determined by the skill of the doctor, who uses special light and oil to examine beneath the skin. By analyzing color, shape, and texture, computers can assist doctors in diagnosing melanoma with greater accuracy. Recent advancements in computer vision allow for distinguishing between skin conditions without specialized devices, using common cameras to capture images, potentially improving early detection [4]. Detecting skin cancer at an early

stage, including melanoma, is vital to improving survival rates, especially in individuals with lighter skin tones. As a result, there is a growing demand for highly accurate automatic skin cancer detection systems. Two types of images are typically captured by these systems: dermatoscopy images captured by specialty equipment in pathology centers, which require dermatologist assessment, and digital images that can be taken at home using standard digital cameras. Nevertheless, it would be possible for individuals to perform skin cancer screenings conveniently and affordably in their own homes by utilizing software that automatically detects skin cancer from digital illustrations, without focusing too much on the Region of Interest (ROI) [5].

Numerous research papers have explored the use of image-processing techniques for the detection of melanoma skin cancer. This approach has several advantages, including the ability to quantify patient changes over time, generate image sets for educational purposes, facilitate rapid image comparison, and potentially offer cost savings [6]. Early diagnosis is paramount for successful skin cancer treatment, commonly achieved through the biopsy method. This process, while effective, presents drawbacks such as pain, time consumption, and delayed results. A viable alternative lies in computer-based technology, offering a more comfortable, cost-effective, and faster means of identifying potential skin cancer issues. Researchers advocate for non-invasive techniques involving digital image capture, preprocessing for analysis readiness, segmentation to isolate the region of interest, and feature extraction, considering factors like color, texture, and shape for distinguishing between benign and malignant lesions. According to the extracted features, the system uses Machine Learning (ML) algorithms like Support Vector Machines (SVMs) or Neural Networks (NNs) to classify the skin lesion as benign or malignant [7]. Deep Learning (DL) has profoundly transformed the ML landscape. It has demonstrated remarkable success in diverse fields, including speech recognition [8], pattern recognition [9], bioinformatics [10]. Moreover, it is increasingly applied to computer-based skin cancer detection, showcasing its potential to enhance accuracy and efficiency in this critical medical domain. Authors in [11] used ML and image processing to detect and classify different types of skin cancer. By implementing preprocessing, color-based segmentation, and feature extraction techniques, they achieved an impressive 96.25% accuracy on the ISIC 2019 Challenge dataset, demonstrating the effectiveness of these methods for early skin cancer detection. Authors in [12] conducted experiments with 640 skin lesion images from the ISIC archive, using 512 for training and the remaining for testing. While the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) performed best, classical ML and image processing methods had their strengths, occasionally detecting melanoma when the CNN could not. To boost performance, they employed majority voting to combine results, improving melanoma detection. This paper introduces an optimized technique for skin cancer diagnosis using CNNs with enhanced Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) for weight and bias selection, reducing the network error. The method was tested on Dermquest and DermIS datasets, outperforming 10 other methods in terms of specificity, accuracy, sensitivity, NPV, and PPV. Current

Computer-Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems face challenges in identifying melanoma due to the complex appearance of nevi.

Authors in [13] introduce an intelligent ROI system utilizing transfer learning, leveraging an improved k-means algorithm for ROI extraction. By focusing on discriminative features and using CNNs with data augmentation, the proposed approach achieved 97.9% and 97.4% accuracy on DermIS and DermQuest datasets, outperforming methods using complete images for classification. Authors in [14] aimed to create a CNN model for skin cancer diagnosis engaging lesion images. Data augmentation was employed as a preprocessing step to enhance model classification robustness. The top-performing model, InceptionResnet, achieved an average accuracy of 91%. Authors in [15] addressed challenges in dermatoscopy image lesion detection by proposing a lightweight skin cancer recognition model based on fine-grained classification principles. The model incorporates feature extraction and discrimination modules, leveraging positive and negative sample pairs. It efficiently extracts discriminative lesion features, upgrading recognition performance with minimal parameters. Additionally, it enables precise lesion area segmentation utilizing a U-Net architecture and migration training strategy, outperforming existing DL-based methods on the ISBI 2016 skin lesion analysis dataset. Authors in [16] addressed the challenge of automating the localization and segmentation of early-stage melanoma skin cancer lesions. They proposed a method that employed Faster Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks (RCNNs) and Fuzzy K-Means (FKM) clustering for segmentation. The approach preprocesses images to enhance visual information, applies Faster-RCNN for feature extraction, and employs FKM for variable-sized lesion segmentation. The method achieved high accuracy of 95.40%, 93.1%, and 95.6% on ISIC-2016, ISIC-2017, and PH2 datasets, respectively, outperforming state-of-the-art approaches and making it a robust tool for skin lesion recognition and segmentation. Authors in [17] used the ISIC2018 dataset with 3533 skin lesions, ameliorating images with ESRGAN and applying CNNs for classification. Multiple transfer learning models, including Resnet50, InceptionV3, and Inception Resnet, were fine-tuned and utilized. The CNN achieved 83.2% accuracy, comparable to other models, highlighting this approach effectiveness at skin lesion detection.

Skin cancer recognition from medical images remains an active research area, with recent focus on DL neural networks. Authors in [18] present 11 CNN architectures trained and tested on the HAM10000 dataset for 7 skin lesion classes. Data augmentation, transfer learning, and fine-tuning addressed imbalance and similarity issues, with DenseNet169 yielding the best results (92.25% accuracy, 93.59% recall, 93.27% F1-score), surpassing state-of-the-art methods. A lightweight version of DenseNet169 was integrated into a mobile Android app for real-time classification of skin lesions and personalized sun exposure recommendations based on UV radiation and skin type. Authors in [19] focused on lung cancer classification using a dataset of 3600 images (224×224 pixels) divided into two classes: malignant and benign. A CNN with fully connected layers was employed, resulting in an accuracy of 86.23% with efficient computations.

This paper proposes a hybrid model for skin cancer classification, comprising image processing techniques, a pre-trained CNN, and a nature-based feature optimization algorithm. The main stages of the current work are:

- Histogram equalization, gamma correction, and white balance adjustment, which are among the preprocessing techniques adopted to enhance the original dataset images.
- Features are extracted by the pre-trained EfficientNetB0 for both the original dataset and its post-enhancement version, which were then serially fused on making the model more flexible in terms of learning and adaptation.
- The extracted features from both scenarios were withdrawn from the last fully connected layer of the EfficientNetB0, and were optimized using ACO.
- The optimized feature vector was then provided as an input to various SVM classifier kernels, and classification was carried out.

II. REGARDING THE CONTENT

This paper proposes a model for skin cancer classification based on the hybrid application of a pre-trained CNN and a nature-based feature optimization algorithm. The proposed model architecture is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Overview of proposed model.

A custom dataset is developed comprising of microscopic images of malignant and benign skin cancer classes, extracted from the ISIC dataset of dermoscopic images. Preprocessing techniques including histogram equalization, gamma correction, and white balance adjustment are applied on the input images with regard to each of their individual R, G, and B channels to make them more prominent, perform color correction, and enhance their overall geometry. The pre-trained CNN EfficientNetB0 is used for pattern recognition and deep feature extraction from the enhanced dataset images. The features elicited by the EfficientNetB0 are then serially fused with the features educed by it when operating on pre-enhancement dataset. This is done to enable the model to absorb details from both the original images and their enhanced versions. To reduce the overall dimension complexity of the fused features, ACO, a nature-based feature selection algorithm, is applied on the latter. ACO eliminates the complexity of the fused feature vector by selecting the most relevant features and discarding the less significant ones. The optimized feature vector is then provided to various SVM classifier kernels to perform classification. The proposed model achieved a maximum accuracy of over 98% while maintaining an excellent prediction speed and reduced training time.

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this work is International Skin Imaging Collaboration (ISIC), which is a global organization dedicated to advancing skin cancer diagnosis and management [20]. The creators have gathered a large collection of skin images, including moles and lesions, for training AI systems to improve diagnosis precision. The primary goal of ISIC is to provide healthcare professionals with cutting-edge tools for early skin cancer identification, which is essential for successful treatment. The ISIC 2019 dataset [21] includes over 25,000 skin lesion images covering various categories, including skin cancer types, benign lesions, and other dermatological conditions. ISIC 2020 also had a significant number of images, but the number of classes and images varied depending on specific challenges. ISIC datasets evolve with new versions and challenges to advance dermatology and skin cancer diagnosis research and development. For this work, a custom dataset is developed comprising microscopic images of malignant and benign skin cancer classes, extracted from the ISIC dataset.

B. Preprocessing

Histogram equalization was first applied at this stage [22]. It improves contrast and brightness by rearranging pixel values within an image to generate a more uniform distribution. This technique is useful for upgrading image quality, particularly in low-contrast or poorly lit situations. To address image quality degradation due to device limitations or unfavorable conditions, we categorized the images based on statistical characteristics and applied Adaptive Gamma Correction (AGC) [23] to dynamically adjust parameters, significantly enhancing contrast. To further ameliorate image quality, we employed a technique known as automatic white balancing [24], which plays a crucial role in digital photography by significantly improving image quality. A novel algorithm, which adjusts adjacent color channels, using luminance and RGB component standard deviation, and includes a light source model for

evaluation, is introduced. Simulations confirm its effectiveness in improving the final image quality. Figure 2 depicts a comparison of the dataset before and after the preprocessing step.

Fig. 2. Comparison of dataset scenarios: (a) Original, (b) preprocessed.

C. Feature Extraction using EfficientNetB0

In the feature extraction step, both the original and the preprocessed datasets pass through the pre-trained EfficientNetB0, and features are extracted from both as shown in Table I. EfficientNetB0 has already learned useful information from datasets like ImageNet, and hence can absorb further details from the given dataset. In this case, it is initialized with pre-trained weights and bias, the extracted features are taken out of the last fully connected layer for optimization and classification. The classifiers are trained by providing the features as input, and give benign/malignant labels as output. The system performance is evaluated by metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. Optionally, the model can be further fine-tuned to provide predictions on the specific skin cancer dataset and its performance can be enhanced, but the proposed work did not focus on CNN fine tuning. Pre-trained CNNs are vastly used to aid early skin cancer detection, ensure ethical and regulatory compliance, and validate the system on diverse datasets to ensure reliability and generalizability [25].

TABLE I. PRE AND POST FEATURE SELECTION OVERVIEW

Original dataset features	Preprocessed dataset features
20,000 × 1,000	20,000 × 1,000

D. Feature Fusion

A key step in image processing is feature fusion, which merges data from several sources to enhance feature representation and discriminative ability for more thorough image analysis. The two basic approaches of feature fusion techniques are the serial and parallel methods. The serial approach integrates features sequentially, while the parallel method does so simultaneously, making use of parallel processing for faster fusion. We extracted deep features from the last fully connected layer of the CNN for both datasets and merged them using the serial-based fusion method. This fused feature vector retains information from the same dataset under two different conditions. We optimized this vector by removing redundant and useless information while preserving important details. This optimization involves data augmentation and three preprocessing techniques on the enhanced dataset, followed by

feature extraction using CNN. At the same time, we provided the dataset before preprocessing to EfficientNetB0. Finally, we serially fused the derived feature vectors from both cases to create a compact 20,000×2,000 feature vector.

E. Feature Selection and Optimization

Swarm intelligence allows us to observe the social behaviors of animals and insects, inspiring creative problem-solving ideas for our daily lives. ACO [26] is a prime example, offering insights into how ants forage for food. Ants communicate by leaving pheromone trails on the ground, guiding other colony members to follow these paths. This unique communication method, known as stigmergy, is essential for the blind ants to coordinate effectively. Pheromones, chemical substances produced by animals, play a crucial role in shaping the behavior of their fellow species members. Equation (1) shows the pheromone level in a graph.

$$\Delta\tau_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{L_k} \\ 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where τ represents the amount of pheromone deposited by an ant on an edge connecting two nodes, i and j , in a graph. The variable k signifies the k th ant in the colony. The term $\Delta\tau_{ij}^k$ represents the change in pheromone levels deposited by the k th ant on that specific edge. The division by L_k is crucial because it reflects the length of the path found by the k th ant. A shorter path found by an ant leads to a higher amount of pheromone being deposited on that path. Essentially, this equation encourages ants to favor shorter paths by depositing more pheromone on them, ultimately helping the colony converge towards finding the shortest and most efficient route.

Equation (1) describes the behavior of a single ant, but we have adopted it for multiple ants in this scenario. Instead of considering a single ant, we now use a summation to calculate the cumulative pheromone level on each edge. Unlike situations where pheromone evaporates, here, pheromone accumulates over time as multiple ants contribute to it. The primary objective remains unchanged: shorter paths receive more pheromone, guiding the colony toward efficient solutions.

$$\tau_{i,j}^k = \sum_{k=1}^m \Delta\tau_{i,j}^k \quad (2)$$

In (2), m denotes the total number of ants. $\tau_{i,j}^k$ represents the current pheromone status and the new pheromone that should be deposited by all ants. Here, vaporization occurs because experiments cycle is performed once by all ants on all the graph edges.

$$\tau_{i,j}^k = (1-\rho) \tau_{i,j}^k + \sum_{k=1}^m \Delta\tau_{i,j}^k \quad (3)$$

In (3), $(1-\rho)$ denotes the current pheromone level, whereas ρ represents the constant value, and defines the evaporation rate. EfficientNetB0 has been employed for feature extraction. The extraction process can result in redundant features that impact both time and accuracy. To address this issue, we have integrated the ACO selection algorithm. ACO helps select only the most relevant features, enhancing both efficiency and accuracy of the proposed model. ACO operates during the feature selection process, leveraging its mechanisms to optimize feature selection and improve the overall performance

of the proposed skin cancer detection system. Table II shows the process of feature selection using ACO.

TABLE II. FEATURE OVERVIEW, PRE AND POST FEATURE SELECTION

Features Pre-ACO	Features Post-ACO
20,000 × 2,000	20,000 × 200

F. Classification

The main aim of the proposed work is to perform skin cancer classification. Predefined labels to images based on their visual content are assigned. To conduct the classification, several SVM classifier kernels are employed namely Linear SVM (LSVM), Quadratic SVM (QSVM), Cubic SVM (CB-SVM), Medium Gaussian SVM (MG-SVM), and Coarse Gaussian SVM (CG-SVM). After extracting the right features from the images in the previous feature optimization step, these features with labels are used to train the SVM classifiers. The SVM kernels learn from these labeled features, picking up on patterns and traits that help identify specific classes. Once they are trained, the SVM classifiers make predictions, and we assess their performance in the next section. This evaluation is based on certain performance measures to see how well each kernel can classify images.

III. THE PROPOSED CLASSIFICATION METHODOLOGY

This paper presents a skin cancer classification model from dermoscopic images that combines EfficientNetB0, a pre-trained CNN, with ACO algorithm. It uses a custom dataset derived from the ISIC dataset, and applies preprocessing techniques for improved image quality. The model extracts features from both the original and enhanced dataset versions, reducing dimension complexity with ACO before classifying the optimized features, using various SVM kernels. A total of four experiments were performed to validate the model based on various dataset and methodology combinations. All the experiments are discussed in detail in the following sections. The system used for all the experimentation runs consisted of an Intel Core i5-4210U CPU with clock speed of 1.70 GHz, 12 GB DDR3 RAM, and 256 GB SSD. All the experiments were performed on MATLAB R2023a.

A. Experiment 1

In the first experiment, the original dataset consisting of 20,000 images was equally divided into two classes based on skin cancer severity, namely Malignant and Benign. These were provided as input to the pre-trained EfficientNetB0. Just like other CNNs, EfficientNetB0 employs its deep layers to extract features from the input images by applying a series of convolutional and pooling operations. These layers learn to detect and represent hierarchical visual patterns from simple edges and textures in early layers to complex infected regions and high-level features in deeper layers. The features are then extracted from the last fully connected layer of EfficientNetB0, named MatMul, organized in the form of a compact 20,000 × 1,000 feature vector, and passed on to SVM classifier and its various kernels for classification. Table III shows the result evaluation of the 5 SVM kernels.

TABLE III. RESULT EVALUATION OF THE SVM CLASSIFIERS

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	MCC (%)
L-SVM	82.73	83.50	82.22	82.86	82.23	83.24	65.46
Q-SVM	93.52	94.43	92.74	93.58	92.74	94.33	87.05
CB-SVM	97.40	98.01	96.82	97.42	96.83	97.99	94.81
MG-SVM	94.11	94.86	93.44	94.15	93.45	94.78	88.22
CG-SVM	80.03	81.23	79.32	80.27	79.33	80.77	60.08

It can be clearly seen that CB-SVM performs better than the other classifiers with an elevated accuracy of 97.40%. Figure 3 shows the confusion matrix of the CB-SVM.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix of the CB-SVM in Experiment 1.

B. Experiment 2

In the second experiment, the original dataset consisting of 20,000 images, was equally divided into two classes based on skin cancer severity, namely Malignant and Benign passed through certain image enhancement and preprocessing steps including color balancing, gamma correction and white balance adjustment. This is done to enhance image quality, make the infected regions more prominent and correct the dullness issue in original dataset images. The improved dataset was then provided as an input to the pre-trained EfficientNetB0. These images were again fed to the EfficientNetB0 and its output to the SVM classifiers. Table IV shows the result evaluation of 5 SVM kernels.

TABLE IV. RESULT EVALUATION OF SVM CLASSIFIERS

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	MCC (%)
L-SVM	78.06	79.71	77.16	78.42	77.16	79.02	56.15
Q-SVM	92.05	93.54	90.82	92.16	90.82	93.34	84.13
CB-SVM	96.77	97.78	95.84	96.80	95.84	97.73	93.56
MG-SVM	92.85	94.42	91.53	92.96	91.54	94.24	85.73
CG-SVM	75.13	77.86	73.82	75.79	73.82	76.58	50.33

CB-SVM again performs better than the rest classifiers with an accuracy of 96.77%. Figure 4 demonstrates the confusion matrix of CB-SVM. It can be noticed that even after preprocessing, the model fails to achieve higher accuracy. Its performance significantly decreases, instead, as compared to Experiment 1 where original dataset is used for experimentation. Therefore, it shows that preprocessing does not have any significant effect on the formulated model.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix of CB-SVM in Experiment 2.

C. Experiment 3

As it is evident from Experiment 1 and Experiment 2, the model is not able to achieve accuracy higher than 97.40%. Even after preprocessing, the performance slightly decrements rather than getting incremented. Therefore, the third experiment implements the feature fusion technique that enables the proposed model to capture complementary information and consider a broader range of image characteristics. This integration of diverse features leads to improved discrimination and generalization, making the model more robust and effective in skin cancer classification and recognition. In this experiment, the features extracted by the EfficientNetB0 from the original dataset in case of Experiment 1 are serially fused with the features extracted by the CNN from the preprocessed dataset of Experiment 2. This fusion leads to the generation of a new feature vector with dimensions of 20000×2000 that has obtained vast information from the same dataset in both original and enhanced condition. This feature vector is then provided to multiple SVM classifier kernels, and classification is performed. Table V shows the result evaluation of 5 SVM kernels.

TABLE V. RESULT EVALUATION OF SVM CLASSIFIERS

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	MCC (%)
L-SVM	85.78	86.14	85.51	85.83	85.52	86.04	71.55
Q-SVM	98.34	99.76	96.99	98.36	97.00	99.75	96.71
CB-SVM	99.01	99.95	98.09	99.01	98.10	99.95	98.03
MG-SVM	98.62	99.87	97.43	98.64	97.43	99.87	97.27
CG-SVM	86.91	87.54	86.44	86.99	86.44	87.38	73.82

It can be seen that after conducting feature fusion, the overall performance of all the classifiers has improved to a great extent and the model has gained a noticeable increment in its performance. All models perform better in case of Experiment 3, but CB-SVM still performs better than the other classifiers with an accuracy exceeding 99%. Figure 5 depicts the confusion matrix of CB-SVM 3.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix of CB-SVM in Experiment 3.

This experiment proves that the proposed model performs better on skin cancer classification when feature fusion is merged with the preprocessing techniques and CNN. Table VI presents the prediction speed and training time taken by all the SVM kernels in case of Experiment 3.

TABLE VI. PREDICTION SPEED AND TRAINING TIME OF SVM CLASSIFIERS

Classifier	Prediction speed (obs/s)	Training time (s)
L-SVM	110	2086.3
Q-SVM	240	858.14
CB-SVM	280	704.58
MG-SVM	160	1206.8
CG-SVM	80	2558.6

D. Experiment 4

After achieving the efficient performance objective, the next goal is to make the model optimized so that it delivers accurate results while maintaining high speed and minimum time consumption. Therefore, the final experiment uses ACO to optimize the fused feature vector formulated in Experiment 3. ACO utilizes a population of artificial ants to explore and evaluate different feature combinations. Ants deposit pheromones to communicate with each other, guiding the search towards more promising feature subsets. Over time, ACO converges towards an optimal or near-optimal feature vector by favoring paths with higher pheromone concentrations, effectively selecting the most relevant features for a given task. In Experiment 4, the ACO is initialized with a population of 10, and the number of iterations is set to 15. The fused $20,000 \times 2,000$ feature vector is passed on as a problem space vector to the algorithm. ACO optimizes the feature

vector to 20,000×200 by selecting only the 200 most relevant features, and discards the rest. Table VII shows the result evaluation of 5 SVM kernels in Experiment 4. Just like the previous experiments, CB-SVM also turns out to be the best performing model in Experiment 4 with an accuracy of 98.43%. Figure 6 shows its confusion matrix f.

TABLE VII. RESULT EVALUATION OF SVM CLASSIFIERS

Classifier	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	MCC (%)
L-SVM	76.91	77.75	76.46	77.10	76.47	77.37	53.83
Q-SVM	97.37	99.41	95.51	97.42	95.51	99.38	94.82
CB-SVM	98.43	99.80	97.12	98.45	97.13	99.79	96.89
MG-SVM	97.98	99.69	96.38	98.01	96.38	99.68	96.01
CG-SVM	82.50	83.71	81.73	82.71	81.73	93.31	65.02

Fig. 6. Confusion matrix of CB-SVM in Experiment 4.

Table VIII illustrates the prediction speed and training time taken by all the SVM kernels in Experiment 4. It can be observed that the time consumed by the classifiers while providing prediction on fused features and the prediction speed were quite improved.

TABLE VIII. RESULTS EVALUATION OF SVM CLASSIFIERS BASED ON PERFORMANCE MEASURES

Classifier	Prediction speed (obs/s)	Training time (s)
L-SVM	860	317.94
Q-SVM	2500	153.66
CB-SVM	2600	125.06
MG-SVM	1500	180.63
CG-SVM	600	388.53

IV. DISCUSSION

The proposed model performed best in case of Experiment 3 with accuracy of CB-SCM exceeding 99%. But this increase in accuracy brought along some downsides in terms of reduced prediction speed and higher training time. Having a classifier with slower prediction speed and longer training time can be disadvantageous in real-time applications because it may lead to delayed responses. It can also increase computational resource requirements, making it less suitable for resource-

constrained environments. Data optimization is crucial as it reduces the dimensionality and noise in the dataset, making the training process more efficient. It also improves the classifier performance by focusing on the most relevant information. This leads to faster training times and quicker predictions, making the classifier more practical for real-time use or large-scale applications. Therefore, ACO feature optimization algorithm is embedded into the proposed model. Its effectiveness can be seen in Experiment 4, which shows that CB-SVM achieved 98.43% accuracy. It may be less impressive than the accuracy of 99.01% in Experiment 3, but is still very high. Therefore, by achieving almost the same performance, ACO helped the model to greatly increase prediction speed as illustrated in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Prediction speed before and after ACO-based feature optimization.

After the implementation of ACO, the model's overall training time also got reduced to a great extent. The time consumed by the classifier kernels on optimized features is far less than that on non-optimized features as shown in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Training time before and after ACO-based feature optimization.

The proposed model indicates that feature fusion when integrated with certain image enhancement techniques and a fine-tuned CNN model, can lead to better accuracy but with compromise on time and speed. Appropriate feature selection algorithms can help solve the issue related to training time and prediction speed and an overall accurate yet slick model can be developed. The future research can focus on leveraging custom

CNN models for skin cancer classification, and exploring better feature selection algorithms to achieve this. Table IX illustrates a comparison of some of the latest existing works with the proposed work. It can be seen that the proposed model excels in terms of accuracy.

TABLE IX. ACCURACY COMPARISON WITH EXISTING WORKS

Reference	Year	Accuracy (%)
[28]	2020	92.83
[31]	2020	95.34
[29]	2021	91.93
[30]	2021	93.7
[27]	2022	87.91
[32]	2023	89.57
Proposed	2023	98.43

V. CONCLUSION

The current paper presents an innovative approach to skin cancer classification, leveraging the synergistic combination of a pre-trained CNN (EfficientNetB0) and a nature-based feature optimization algorithm (ACO). Through the development of a custom dataset and meticulous preprocessing techniques, the model excels in extracting meaningful features from microscopic malignant and benign skin cancer images. Feature fusion from both the original and enhanced images significantly enhances model capacity for pattern recognition. By applying ACO for dimensionality reduction, the model optimizes feature selection, ultimately resulting in a highly accurate classification system, achieving an accuracy rate exceeding 98%. Finally, this accuracy is attained without compromising prediction speed and training time, making it a promising tool for real-world applications in dermatology and medical image analysis.

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Analyzing Embankment Displacement: PVD and Vacuum Consolidation with Sheet Pile Protection

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ABSTRACT

The global widespread adoption of Prefabricated Vertical Drains (PVD) in conjunction with vacuum consolidation is driven by its robust and cost-efficient attributes. However, this construction method is not without challenges, as it has been linked to substantial displacements, posing risks to adjacent structures. Addressing such concerns in a Vietnamese road construction project, this study focuses on the innovative contribution of sheet pile protection as a highly effective solution. Utilizing numerical analysis with an anisotropic model, we examine the impact of sheet pile protection on embankment displacement. Through comparative analysis with field data, our study demonstrates the remarkable efficacy of the sheet pile method in significantly reducing both vertical and lateral settlements. Acting as a protective membrane, it effectively counters suction from the PVD vacuum zone. These findings make a substantial contribution to the field, providing engineers handling similar structural protection scenarios with invaluable insights and a novel approach to mitigating displacements associated with PVD and vacuum consolidation.

Keywords-PVD; vacuum consolidation; sheetpile; lateral displacement

I. INTRODUCTION

PVD, in conjunction with vacuum consolidation, has been widely embraced for its efficient and cost-effective approach in expediting consolidation processes. However, this construction method is not without its challenges, often resulting in substantial lateral and vertical displacements, thereby posing potential risks to adjacent structures. Authors in [1] identified a critical tension cracking zone linked to lateral embankment displacement during vacuum application. Complementing this, authors in [2] conducted field measurements to unravel factors influencing lateral displacement, including construction rate, consolidation rate, and loading. Numerous laboratory tests, including the use of modified triaxial test devices [3, 4, 5], have explored the lateral displacement associated with this technique. Additionally, several studies have proposed straightforward techniques for predicting such displacement. Despite the wealth of analytical [8-10] and numerical [1, 6, 7,

12, 13] studies examining vertical and lateral displacements resulting from PVD with vacuum consolidation, a critical aspect remains largely unexplored: the identification of countermeasures to effectively mitigate these substantial displacements. In the analysis of the Bachiem road construction case study, a strategic solution emerged to mitigate displacements linked to embankment construction, employing steel sheet piles. The efficacy of this approach was validated through field measurements, affirming the significant reduction in lateral displacement and the consequent protection of nearby structures. A comprehensive numerical analysis delved into the reinforcement method, uncovering that the sheet pile wall adeptly obstructed pore pressure and applied stresses, ultimately leading to a notable decrease in lateral displacement. These findings not only offer crucial insights for engineers grappling with similar challenges but also furnish compelling evidence supporting the adoption of sheet pile solutions as a protective measure for neighboring structures in their projects.

II. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The Bachiem project, situated 20 km east of Hochiminh City in southern Vietnam, involved ground improvement for a road using Prefabricated Vertical Drains (PVD) in conjunction with vacuum consolidation, as depicted in Figure 1. The project is located on a soft clay deposit from the Saigon river with depth varying from 10 to 30 m depth. These conditions posed a risk of substantial settlement after construction, necessitating ground improvement to facilitate consolidation and prevent damage to road structures during service. A comprehensive account of the project details can be found in [12]. However, a significant challenge emerged due to the proximity of nearby structures, situated very close to the construction site.

Fig. 1. Project location.

Fig. 2. Construction site with sheet pile protection.

As depicted in Figure 2, the proximity of residential structures to the embankment, with spacing ranging from 2.0 to 6.0 m, raises concerns about potential damage during construction. To address this issue, a solution involving the installation of steel sheet piles at the embankment toe was proposed, extending to a depth of 18 m to protect the nearby buildings. Figure 2 illustrates the on-site implementation of the sheet pile, with the treated zone on the left featuring a geomembrane cover at the surface. The road width was 19.5 m, with a 2.3 m height. The soil profile included layer 1a,

consisting of soft to very soft clay from the ground to a depth of 20.5 m, layer 1b with medium clay from 20.5 to 24.0 m, and layer 2 comprising sandy clay from 24.0 to 30.0 m. Ground treatment involved a PVD triangle pattern with a 1.0 m spacing, reaching a depth of 15.0 m. Inclinerometers were strategically installed at the toe of the embankment on both the left and right-hand sides, providing critical monitoring points for lateral displacement of the construction process.

III. DISPLACEMENT MEASUREMENT DATA

As evident from Figure 3(a), notable lateral displacement was observed at the end of treatment, particularly on the left side where no reinforcement was implemented. The maximum lateral displacement reached almost 0.5 m towards the embankment, signifying the influence of vacuum pressure inducing suction and creating a similar isotropic state for the treated soil elements beneath the embankment. This phenomenon aligns with the findings reported in laboratory tests and field measurements [2, 4]. Interestingly, this behavior contrasts with conventional embankments subjected to surcharge preloading, where lateral displacement typically moves outward from the embankment due to the imposed stresses from the surcharge load.

Fig. 3. Lateral displacements at the end of treatment: (a) at the left side of embankment without any reinforcement, (b) at the right side of embankment with sheet pile reinforcement.

Conversely, the field measurements from the right side (Figure 3(b)), reinforced with sheet pile, demonstrated minimal displacement, highlighting the effective role of sheet pile in mitigating the impact of embankment construction enhanced with the PVD vacuum technique. Figure 4(b) illustrates that the lateral displacement near the sheet pile wall reached a maximum value of 0.015 m toward the embankment, a 33 times reduction compared to the displacement on the left-hand side. It is worth noting that the effectiveness of sheet pile reinforcement may be largely dependent on the depth of treatment. The treatment depth was 15.0 m, while the length of the sheet pile wall extended to 18.0 m. The data presented in Figure 3(a) show a rapid reduction in lateral displacement on

the right side when the treatment depth reached from 10.0 to 15.0 m, suggesting that this depth range can function as a zone restraining displacement for the sheet pile. Consequently, the lateral displacement of the sheet pile exhibited minimal values, as observed in Figure 4(b).

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

To comprehensively assess the effectiveness of the reinforcement method, this study conducted numerical simulations. The employed approach involved the anisotropic model of [14] incorporating the rotation of the yield surface, accounting for soil anisotropy. This choice is justified by the characteristics of clay particles and their flocculation during the natural consolidation process, making an anisotropic model a reasonable representation. The parameters used for model validation are detailed in Table I. λ is the compression index, κ is the recompression index, α is the size and inclination of the yield surface, β and μ are the material parameters controlling the rotation rate when yield surface rotate toward direction of applied load, and M is the critical stress ratio in compression (M_c). The critical stress ratio in extension, M_e , was based on the generalization of three dimensional stress trajectories of M assuming dependence on Lod 's angle [15].

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF THE ANISOTROPIC MODEL

Parameter	λ	κ	α	β	μ	M
Value	0.60	0.075	0.62	0.856	5.0	1.3

The constitutive model was implemented into ABAQUS using a UMAT (user-defined material) model. Model validation involved a comparison with the compression and extension results of CkoU, as illustrated in Figures 4 and 5. The soil sample underwent initial K_0 consolidation to a mean effective pressure of 119.0 kPa, followed by shear processes. Figure 4 presents a comparison of stress paths, while Figure 5 illustrates the stress-strain relationship. These comparisons serve to highlight the efficacy of the anisotropic model in accurately capturing the stress-strain behavior and stress paths within the current soft soil.

Fig. 4. Comparison of stress path between the simulated and the experimental results.

Fig. 5. Comparison of stress-strain between the simulated and the experimental results.

Moreover, the parameters for each soil layer were derived from the details presented in [12], including values such as maximum past pressure, over consolidation ratio, vertical and horizontal permeability for each layer, and the permeability assigned to the treated zone. It is important to highlight that the current approach involved employing the same simulation method for the PVD treated zone, which was replaced with an equivalent soil layer possessing similar properties. However, the vertical permeability for this layer was modified based on [16]. The loading sequence was also outlined in the study by [12]. The sheet pile type NS-SP-IV had sectional area $A = 225.5 \text{ cm}^2/\text{m}$ and moment of inertia $I = 56,700 \text{ cm}^4/\text{m}$. The simulation for sheet pile employed beam elements with the same value of AI .

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Figure 6, a comparison is presented between the settlement values obtained from the Finite Element Method (FEM) results and the actual field data. The FEM results exhibit a commendable agreement with the measured settlement values, affirming the appropriateness of the simulation in accurately capturing the settlement behavior of the treated embankment.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the settlement at the center of the embankment between the FEM results and field measurement.

Fig. 7. Comparison of the lateral displacement between the FEM results and field measurements: (a) at the left side of the embankment without any reinforcement, (b) at the right side of the embankment with sheet pile reinforcement.

Figure 7 provides a comparison between the simulated lateral displacements and the field measurement data. The Figure demonstrates that the current simulation effectively captures the lateral displacement observed in the field data. Furthermore, the simulation successfully characterizes the influence of the sheet pile wall in reducing lateral displacements. As depicted in Figure 8, the pore pressure distribution at the end of the construction state (date 240) highlights the efficacy of the sheet pile wall. On the right-hand side of the embankment, the sheet pile effectively obstructed negative pore pressure. Conversely, on the left-hand side, the pore pressure gradually diminished outward from the toe of the embankment. Additionally, Figure 8 illustrates that the maximum negative pore pressure induced by the vacuum, reaching -65 kPa, was distributed across almost the entire treated zone with PVD. This observation underscores the effectiveness of the ground improvement method.

Fig. 8. Pore pressure distribution after treatment.

Supporting the effectiveness of the sheet pile wall, Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the distribution of vertical effective stress before and after treatment. Notably, the right side exhibits minimal variation in vertical stress, particularly near the ground surface, in comparison to the left side. This evidence strongly suggests that the sheet pile wall on the right side of the embankment efficiently shields against the transfer of stress from the construction site to the adjacent zone.

Fig. 9. Vertical effective stress before treatment.

Fig. 10. Vertical effective stress after treatment.

The sheet pile wall serves as an effective barrier, successfully mitigating the distribution of both pore pressure and vertical stress. Consequently, the prevention of vertical and lateral displacements is evident, as illustrated in Figures 11 and 12. Figure 12 indicates a common tendency of lateral displacement to move inward toward the embankment on both the right and left sides. Notably, the right side, particularly at the embankment toe where the sheet pile is located, exhibits significantly less displacement than the left side.

Fig. 11. Vertical displacements of the embankment.

Fig. 12. Lateral displacements of the embankment.

VI. CONCLUSION

The comprehensive analysis and simulations conducted in this study provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the ground improvement methods, particularly the implementation of sheet pile walls in combination with Prefabricated Vertical Drains (PVD) and vacuum consolidation. The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of this study:

- The sheet pile wall effectively obstructs negative pore pressure, contributing to the success of the ground improvement method.
- The sheet pile wall efficiently shields against stress transfer, resulting in minimal variations in vertical stress.
- The sheet pile wall serves as a barrier, successfully mitigating both pore pressure and vertical stress distributions, leading to the prevention of vertical and lateral displacements for the adjacent zone.

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A Binary Object Detection Pattern Model to Assist the Visually Impaired in detecting Normal and Camouflaged Faces

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a novel Binary Object Detection Pattern Model (BODPM) to detect objects with face key points and recognize them using the KERAS dataset. The proximity and accuracy of the recognized items were evaluated using computer vision techniques. The object recognition time interval and duration were recorded and stored permanently in a database, and the information was communicated to the visually impaired user as voice output. The normal face, without wearing a mask, was identified using binary patterns with proximity detection. Camouflaged objects were detected in a maximum probability range of 100%. The proposed method was tested, calculating accuracy and score, and compared with existing models, showcasing remarkable performance. The proposed method of normal and camouflage detection is a novel prediction with proximity analysis of objects in a frame.

Keywords-binary object detection pattern model; KERAS dataset; visually impaired; computer vision; camouflaged object detection; parameter assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Visually Impairment (VI) is a complicated challenge that may lead to unemployment in most areas of work around the world [1]. A native dataset was used in [2] to record and support users to determine objects in front of the visitor office of a visually impaired person. With the use of VI glasses, the visually impaired user was able to recognize visitors to their office and append user information to the native dataset, such as their name, timeslot of arrival, and proximity [3]. This will make it easier for visually impaired people to find employment, as they can record and keep visitor information on hand [4]. The primary objective of this study was to design and construct a framework to identify concealed objects and aid people with VI. This was achieved using the extensively recognized dataset from the KERAS repository [9]. This dataset was used to determine the spatial separation between the objects and to determine their respective designations. The study emphasized on the detection of the proximity of objects to VI individuals, gauging the degree of proximity as a percentage and establishing their significance in predictive analysis. Evaluation metrics, including accuracy and F-score, were considered when subjected to classifier tests. Details concerning user, time allocation, and related information were transmitted as audio input to the speakers. Simultaneously, this information was

logged and integrated into the native dataset for update purposes. The scope of this study was limited to the facilitation of people with VI, helping them recognize familiar and unfamiliar individuals or objects and gauging the spatial intervals between them through the application of computer vision techniques. Such an assistive device not only expands the vocational prospects of visually impaired people but also contributes to improving their overall quality of life. In [5], a multitasking CV model was built in hybridization with a segmentation process at training levels. A similar model was also presented in [6], where the computer vision models Random Forest Tree (RFT) (85%), Decision Tree (DT) (80.8%), and K-NN (74.8%) showed good results, but unlike [5], without conducting a separate indoor and outdoor analysis. Table I shows previous studies and proposed models along with their identified gaps.

The reviewed studies were significantly behind in some areas, although they confirmed that more efficient models could not detect objects, faces, and proximity at the same time. These research gaps included the following significant factors: (1) Merged or interlaced objects were difficult to identify [16], (2) could not handle collective problems such as objects, faces, and proximal detections simultaneously [7], and (3) the actual implementation could not be modeled due to the global nature

of the COCO dataset [8]. Furthermore, existing models need to accommodate a compatible database such as KERAS [9]. As a result, these gaps must be filled in the proposed model, which should be implemented, tested, and compared with existing models to determine its performance.

TABLE I. EXISTING MODELS AND METHODS

Ref.	Models and Methods	Gaps identified
[10]	Constructed a sequence of actions employing computer vision models	The demand for substantial computational intelligence was noted
[11]	Explored the significance of computer vision in the realm of security and its practical applications.	Stressed the necessity for an object detection-centric safety protocol
[12]	Assessed the effectiveness of distinct classifiers, such as k-means, kNN, DT, and RFT models.	Anticipated enhanced performance from hybrid models when handling complex images
[13]	Investigated challenges and importance of interfacing with smart devices for object tracking, safety, and prediction accuracy	Highlighted limitations of the COCO dataset, prompting the need for updates or hybrid datasets
[14]	Examined a dataset to categorize collected images and segment them into distinct components	Identified the requirement for additional preprocessing for facial object images
[15]	Created an environment and motion-based facial identification system capable of alerting users and detecting concealed objects	Expressed the potential for enhancing proximity and tracking mechanisms in the models
[16]	Employing the You Only Look Once v3 (YOLOv3) model, analogous face detection for animals was conducted, with a specific focus on pigs.	The closeness percentage, however, decreased as the pigs' separation from the source device grew. As a result, the relationship between proximity percentage and separation between the items was inverse
[17]	Used in traffic management and control	The proximity percentage of detection was very low
[18]	Explored techniques in image processing and visual perception to enhance the experience for individuals with VIs, offering improved input at a more affordable expense.	The cost of building the model was comparatively high.

II. METHODOLOGY

Computer vision is an advanced technology that offers users valuable information and experience [20]. Its diverse applications include tasks such as drone image processing analysis and the development of educational visual aids. In the context of this study, the potential of this technology was harnessed to assist people with VI in object recognition and information retrieval. This was achieved using the KERAS dataset [21] in conjunction with information from other global datasets. In [22-23], a mobile platform was designed to both detect the proximity of objects and accurately identify them. This platform facilitated real-time object recognition and determination of source distance. However, it faced limitations in detecting camouflaged or masked faces directly in front of the user. The user would receive an auditory message detailing the identified and recorded object, excluding those that were camouflaged. This study addressed this limitation by devising a multiphase framework model, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Model structure for implementing camouflaged object detection.

The system incorporates a webcam or pinhole camera into smart blind glasses, which the visually impaired user employs to capture images. Alternatively, in the scenario of IoT-enabled glasses, a pi camera can be used [24]. This camera processes the image and employs box-shaped face detection techniques to identify blind spots on the object. The KERAS dataset is used to associate the recognized box face with the identification and labeling of the objects. The identified object is transmitted to the processing unit of the smart system, where it is stored as an output along with contextual information, timestamp, and date of detection. Subsequently, the text-to-speech conversion tool [25] converts the image data into textual form and the result is audibly relayed through internal or external speakers. BODPM introduces an innovative concept comprising three primary phases:

- Training the model for object detection
- Detecting normal or camouflaged objects
- Evaluating parameters and providing speech-based assistance

Figure 2 shows the framework for these three phases. In the initial phase of object recognition, the visually impaired individual captures an image using his smart blind glasses placed within his usual field of vision. The acquired image undergoes additional analysis to identify the specific boundary that outlines the face of the detected object. This identification process involves a comparison with the KERAS dataset used in TensorFlow-based object detection methods [26], particularly within models grounded in computer vision. The result of this identification becomes an integral part of the output from the first phase, serving as input for the subsequent phase focused on detecting either normal or camouflaged objects. Using the visual patterns established in the second phase, a novel algorithm called the Binary Object Detection Pattern Model (BODPM) is employed. This algorithm trains the models and differentiates between normal and camouflaged objects. The findings of the object detection phase, along with associated information, are subsequently forwarded to the final phase of the model.

Fig. 2. The Binary Object Detection Pattern Model (BODPM) framework.

Within this phase, an integrated proximity detection algorithm [27-28] calculates the distance between recognized objects and the visually impaired user. This model also records nearby objects, along with essential details such as the date and time of identification, during the transition from textual information to voice-based output in the text-to-voice conversion phase [25]. Here, the conversion engine processes the textual information and delivers the result audibly to the user. In a broader context, BODPM comprises two key phases, each underpinned by the following algorithms.

Figure 3 shows the initialization of the learning rate, epochs for time measurement, and batch size with two categories of detections, including with and without mask, respectively. The image is captured from KERAS to preprocess and training. The image is converted into a matrix form with textual components. The textual components are further segregated into binary data to train the models on the x and y-axis of the image to be captured. Thus, the binarization associates the best features to be captured for a better augmentation of the data captured from the image. Then, the models from the TensorFlow and Keras datasets are used to evaluate the parameters *AveragePooling2D*, *Dense*, and *Dropout*, respectively. The initial base and face objects are loaded and trained with the models. Training is a continuous process, extended until further training is not required. If the model is trained, the model is compiled with loss and optimizer analysis. The model is tested and evaluated using the accuracy measure. Then the fitness function is applied and the model prediction is initiated. Finally, the trained models are evaluated and the efficiency was calculated. After initiating the fitness function to train the model, the object detection model was initiated as shown in Figure 3.

```

Algorithm Camouflaged Model Train (CMT)
Step 1: Initialize the Learning Rate, Epochs for Time Measurement, and Batch Size.
Step 2: Create a list with two categories 'Normal' and 'Camouflaged'.
Step 3: Capture the images from the KERAS dataset and preprocess them.
Step 4: Identify the image matrix in text form.
Step 5: Convert the text images to Binary data with training models in the x and y axes.
Step 6: Generate the image data for data augmentation including the following: = {rotation_range, zoom_range, width_shift_range, height_shift_range, shear_range, horizontal_flip, fill_mode}.
Step 7: Load the TensorFlow-based KERAS models with input shapes and size.
Step 8: Load the head model with evaluations including AveragePooling2D, Dense, Dropout.
Step 9: Load the initial image parameters for base objects.
Step 10: Test if the objects were trained. If Yes, no further training, else training is required.
Step 11: If the model is trained, compile the model with loss and optimizer analysis.
Step 12: Evaluate the model testing for Accuracy.
Step 13: Apply the fitness function and train the model using validation data.
Step 14: Test epochs until the end of the batch size.
Step 15: Apply the model and predict the arguments.
Step 16: Train the model in the background until detection is completed.
Step 17: Evaluate accuracy and plot the loss in training.
Step 18: Calculate Train_efficiency : = Loss / Accuracy.
Step 19: Plot the image and display the results.
Step 20: Terminate when object detection is completed.
End CMT
    
```

Fig. 3. Camouflaged Model Train (CMT) algorithm for initiating object recognition.

As shown in Figure 4, the initial image is captured from the video stream of a local web camera or any external device. FaceNet is used to detect the shape of the image. The confidence level is calculated from the image matrix. The bounding box for the object is measured using the product of *shape_detections* × *array_matrix*. The size of the object is then calculated from the selection points on the image face. The preprocessed image is converted from BGR to RGB using color and resizing options. Later, the detected faces are identified based on the user list and the use model algorithm to detect protective items. The path was assigned to calculate the weight to find key facial points. In the follow-up process, when the object comes inside the frame, the mask detection model is loaded to identify the video device and load the stream of bytes. The individual frame of the image is loaded and resized to the frame of the image based on visual patterns. The camouflaged_object_detection fitness function is applied to the captured frame to identify the parameters in the start and end points of the x and y axes (*xstart*, *ystart*, *xend*, *yend*, respectively) to identify objects and draw bounding boxes. The face is tested if it is normal or camouflaged. If normal, then the object is indicated with a bounding box in red color, else the

green color is used to indicate the camouflaged image. The *probability_of_mask* is calculated by finding the maximum of *mask* and *without_mask* multiplied by 100. The output bounding box is adjusted based on the detected object. Then, the color changes are modified based on the camouflaged or normal face. Finally, the probability percentage and the accuracy are displayed based on the detected object. The result is also saved in the native dataset to be used for future reference and verification by the visually impaired person, and is also a source of visitors at a particular point in time.

```

Algorithm Camouflaged_Object_Detection (COD)
Step 1: Capture an image from an external camera.
Step 2: Detect the face as shape using facenet.
Step 3: The confidence level is calculated from the image matrix.
Step 4: Calculate bounding_box: = shape_detections × array_matrix.
Step 5: Calculate the size of the object based on the selection points of the image face
Step 6: Preprocess image from BGR to RGB using color and resizing options.
Step 7: Detect faces based on the list of users and use the model algorithm to detect protective items.
Step 8: Assign path and weight to calculate face_keypoints.
Step 9: Load mask detection model.
Step 10: Identify the video device and load the stream of bytes.
Step 11: Read an individual frame from the image.
Step 12: Resize the frame of the image based on visual patterns.
Step 13: Apply the Camouflaged_Object_Detection fitness function on the captured frame.
Step 14: Identify the parameters in the start and the end points of the x and y axes.
Step 15: Identify the object and draw the bounding box.
Step 16: Test if the face is normal or camouflaged.
Step 17: If normal, indicate the bounding box in red color, else in green.
Step 18: Calculate Probability_of_Mask: = Max(mask, without_mask) × 100.
Step 19: Adjust the output bounding box based on the detected object.
Step 20: Modify color changes based on camouflaged or normal face.
Step 21: Display the probability percentage and accuracy based on the detected object.
End COD

```

Fig. 4. Camouflaged Object Detection (COD) algorithm for object recognition.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The proposed model was compared with existing models. Previous studies showed that the RFT, DT, and kNN models yielded accuracies of 85, 80.8, and 74.8%, respectively. The proposed model was tested using different image parameters. The model was implemented in Python coupled with TensorFlow. Figure 5 shows a preliminary object detection stage.

As shown in Figure 5, the proposed model demonstrated its efficiency in recognizing specific individuals in two distinct locations. Both the timestamp of the visitor's presence and the proximity of the human subject were logged, exhibiting an

improved performance rate of 82%. Additionally, all relevant data were systematically stored in a dedicated database. The proposed model surpassed the DT (80.8%) and kNN (74.8%) models. Furthermore, even the RFT model's 85% accuracy was exceeded in outdoor detections, achieving an impressive peak accuracy level of 98%. Figure 6 shows that the proximity performance was higher. The selected entities were the potted plant and humans, with a peak performance of 98%, surpassing existing models. The proposed model also recorded the object's date and time. Other tests explored the effect of merging two objects, one of which was a person. While the individual was identified with a proximity efficiency of 65%, the potted plant was detected with a proximity efficiency of 77%. Consequently, as shown in Figure 7, efficiency decreases when two items are combined.

Fig. 5. Object detection using the proposed model. (one of the authors captured during the detection process).

Fig. 6. Object detection in an outside environment (the participants gave permission to show their faces).

Fig. 7. Object detection of mixed objects.

The proposed model outperformed the existing models with an average difference of 1%, which is a considerable improvement. The experiments demonstrated that the entities could be recognized and locally detected without any systemic mistakes. As shown in Figure 8, the camouflaged detection was completed with a normal face indicated by the red bounding box, and the proximity detection accuracy was 100% for direct faces and 99.51% for faces that were turned. Figure 9 shows that face detection in masked form is indicated with a green bounding box, achieving 100% proximity efficiency. The proposed model was examined and implemented to identify that it could fit into any computer vision model. The proposed hybrid model was able to identify camouflaged faces and objects, outperforming existing models. The model was capable of identifying the objects and faces in both inside and outside environments with remarkable efficiency.

Fig. 8. Object detection in the normal face with red bounding box (one of the authors captured during the detection process).

Fig. 9. Object and face recognition after masking the face (the participants gave permission to show their faces).

This study designed and implemented a novel framework called BODPM, which works as a hybrid of existing models. The proposed framework covered three aspects, including image capture, recognition, and proximity detection at the same time. In addition, this model also recorded the time slots in conjunction with the system information. Another noteworthy result of this study was the detection of camouflaged faces. Table II shows the overall comparative analytics of the proposed object detection process with the existing models. The proposed BODPM model outperformed RFT, DT, and kNN, with increased performance in positive measures such as accuracy and F-score, and reduced error rate.

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE ANALYTICS OF BODPM AND EXISTING MODELS IN OBJECT DETECTION

Model	Accuracy	Error Rate	F-score
RFT	85%	0.67	0.83
DT	80.8%	0.76	0.78
kNN	74.8%	0.91	0.65
Proposed BODPM	98%	0.43	0.98

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the experimental results, the main objective of introducing an enhanced model was successfully realized, exhibiting superior performance over existing models. The proposed BODPM model demonstrated an outstanding peak performance of 98%, which has the potential to serve as a benchmark for subsequent research endeavors. In particular, both indoor and outdoor object detections achieved significantly high levels of reliability. Remarkably, the proposed framework effectively addressed all the shortcomings of previous models, aligning with the intended objectives. The integration of IoT-enabled devices would facilitate the proficient management of substantial quantities of image and video data, addressing a current limitation of the model. Consequently, this inventive framework has proven highly successful in providing a pertinent solution for individuals with VI, while also holding the potential to advance object recognition alongside proximity detection in the future.

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A Study on the Influence of aging of the Butt-welded PE100 SDR11 on Shore A Hardness and Tensile Strength

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of an experimental study on the influence of aging on the shore A hardness and tensile strength of butt-welded PE100 SDR11 pipeline joints with a nominal diameter of 125 mm and wall thickness of 11.40 mm used in natural gas distribution transportation. For the experimental determination, 12 samples were taken from the body of the pipe, 9 of which were taken from the area of the butt-welded joint. The test tubes were divided into 3 groups of 4 pieces each (1 unwelded test tube and 3 welded test tubes). Using the Arrhenius method, the test tubes in 2 groups were given artificial aging treatments of 10 and 20 years. Subsequently, all 12 test tubes were tested for shore A hardness and tensile strength. For the welded samples, an increase in tensile strength was observed with increasing aging time by 6.5% for the 10-year aged samples and by 6.16% for the 20-year aged samples. For the unwelded samples, the tensile strength decreased by 3.57% for 10-year aging and increased by 5.84% for 20-year aging. Artificial aging of 10 and 20 years of natural gas transmission and distribution pipelines did not considerably influence the Shore A hardness values, as they were in the medium/soft hardness range.

Keywords-polyethylene; pressure welding; tensile strength; shore A hardness

I. INTRODUCTION

Polyethylene (PE) has become one of the most widely used thermoplastic materials due to its many technical and economic advantages compared to other materials in this range [1-15]. The major advantage of this plastic material is that it can be repeatedly softened and reshaped under heating without changing its core structure and properties, [12, 26, 20]. The assortment diversity, the multitude of practical applications, and the fact that it is easy to recycle have imposed the use of PE in many industrial fields, such as drinking water distribution networks for domestic and industrial consumers, natural gas distribution networks, irrigation and water management networks, sewerage systems, protection systems for electrical cables, transport of food or industrial liquids, protection pipes in thermally pre-insulated systems, etc. [2, 22, 28]. The safe use of PE pipes and fittings in the construction of natural gas distribution networks is a constant concern, supported by the

results of research into the knowledge and continuous improvement of plastic materials, their manufacturing technologies, non-demountable welding assembly processes (hot air jet welding, portable extruder welding, butt welding, electrofusion welding, polyfusion welding), and their quality control methods [2-4]. In this context, the tensile strength behavior of samples taken from pipes obtained by butt-welding pipes made of PE100 is studied in [22]. Tensile tests were performed on welded and unwelded samples, using various values of crosshead velocity, ranging from 5 to 500 mm/min. Increasing crosshead speed resulted in increasingly higher elasticity values for both types of test tubes. Regardless of the crosshead speed values, higher tensile strength values were obtained for the welded samples than for the unwelded ones. In [23], the way the parameters of the PE100 SDR17 (SDR: Standard Dimension Ratio) PN10 pipe electrofusion welding influence the mechanical characteristics of the welded assembly was studied. One of the studied parameters was the

cooling speed of the welded joint, which decisively influenced the mechanical characteristics of the welded joint. In [24], the influence of the mechanical properties of high density PE pipes, which have been subjected to the artificial aging process, was presented. Artificial aging was carried out by heating the pipes with hot air at 90 ± 1 °C for up to 8 cycles, each consisting of 7 days. The mechanical properties of the artificially aged pipes were determined by tensile testing. It was found that tensile strength improved along with increasing aging time.

The novelty of the current paper is the experimental study on the influence of aging on the shore A hardness and tensile strength of butt-welded butt joints of PE100 SDR11 pipes with a nominal diameter of 125 mm and a wall thickness of 11.40 mm.

II. SHORE A TENSILE AND HARDNESS STRENGTH TESTING

A. Tensile Test

Tensile testing is widely used to determine the in-service performance of various materials and welded assemblies [17-19]. Tensile tests were carried out on 9 welded and 3 unwelded tubes taken from pipelines used in natural gas transmission and distribution, obtained through butt welding of pipes made of PE100SDR11. Out of the total of 12 tensile tested tubes, 4 were artificially aged by 10 years and 4 by 20 years.

1) Preparation of the Test Tubes

The samples were taken from pipelines used for the transmission and distribution of natural gas, obtained by butt welding pipes made of PE100SDR11, with a nominal diameter of 125 mm and a wall thickness of 11.40 mm, using the George Fisher TM315 welding machine. Figure 1 presents the steps of butt pressure welding of PE100SDR11 pipes and the main elements and components of the George Fisher TM315 welding machine.

Fig. 1. Butt pressure welding of PE100SDR11 pipes: (a) milling the pipe butts, (b) heating the pipe butts to welding temperature, (c) welding the pipe butts: 1- pipe, 2- adjustable bins, 3- milling cutter, 4- heated plate, 5- welded joint.

Figure 2 shows the pipeline used for the transport and distribution of natural gas, obtained by butt-welding pipes made of PE100SDR11, from which tensile test tubes were taken for experimental determination. According to SR EN ISO

527-2-2012 type 1A [26], we took the 12 samples shown in Figure 3 from the pipe shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Pipe made of PE100 SDR11: 1, 2 - pipe, 3 - welded assembly.

Fig. 3. Tensile test tubes made of PE100 SDR11.

The test tubes were split into 3 groups of 4 pieces (1 non-welded and 3 welded tubes). Using the Arrhenius method, the samples in 2 groups were subjected to artificial aging treatments by 10 and 20 years by exposure at a temperature of 110 °C for 170 and 340 hours, respectively.

2) Performing the Tensile Test

Tensile testing of the 12 samples was performed on the Mecmesin Multitest 10-I Universal Testing Machine (UTM) (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Tensile test on the Mecmesin Multitest 10-i UTM.

3) Shore A Hardness Test

The hardness measurement on the 12 samples was performed using the Sauter HDA 100-1 digital hardness tester depicted in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Shore A hardness test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Tensile Strength Test

Figure 6 shows the PE100 SDR 11 samples after performing the tensile tests. The welded samples broke in the thermally influenced area and the unwelded ones elongated up to 500 mm, (maximum stroke of the UTM). The graphical results of the tensile tests for all the samples are illustrated in Figures 7-9.

Fig. 6. PE100 SDR 11 samples after the tensile test.

Figure 10 shows the values of the tensile strengths and Figure 11 the values of the elongations at break obtained after the tensile testing of the 12 samples. Analyzing Figure 10, it can be observed that artificial aging increases the fracture toughness of butt-welded joints of PE100 SDR11 pipes with a nominal diameter of 125 mm and a wall thickness of 11.40 mm. The best results obtained (24.12-24.71 MPa) were for samples artificially aged by 10 years. In the case of non-welded samples, the maximum value of the tensile strength was 24.17 MPa and was obtained for samples artificially aged by 20 years. For the welded samples, artificial aging by 10

years resulted in an increase in tensile strength from 1.28 to 1.51 MPa while artificial aging by 20 years resulted in an increase in tensile strength from 0.46 to 1.43 MPa. Summarizing, the tensile strength of the welded samples is 1.92 to 10% higher than the tensile strength of unwelded samples.

Fig. 7. Tensile test charts of non-artificially aged samples: (a) sample 1 (unwelded), (b) samples 2, 3, 4 (welded).

Fig. 8. Tensile test plots of samples artificially aged by 10 years: (a) sample 5 (unwelded), (b) samples 6, 7, 8 (welded).

Fig. 9. Tensile test plots of samples artificially aged by 20 years: (a) sample 9 (unwelded), (b) samples 10, 11, 12 (welded).

Fig. 10. Tensile strength values for samples tested in tension.

Analyzing Figure 11, it can be concluded that artificial aging causes a decrease of 6.45 to 88.89% in the elongation at break for butt pressure welded joints of PE100 SDR11 pipes. In the case of non-welded samples tested in tension, artificial aging resulted in an insignificant decrease in elongation at break from 0 to 0.34%. For the welded samples, artificial aging by 10 years resulted in a decrease in elongation at break from 1 to 123 mm while artificial aging by 20 years resulted in a decrease in elongation at break from 16 to 82 mm. The aging of butt-welded butt joints of PE100 SDR11 pipes was found to significantly influence the tensile behavior of pipelines used for the transport and distribution of natural gas. This drawback was highlighted by tracking the effects of temperature aging

without quantifying other elements such as pressure (internal and external) or chemical elements that can affect the life-span of polyethylene pipes.

Fig. 11. Tensile elongation at break values for samples tested in tension.

B. Shore A Hardness Test

Figure 12 illustrates the Shore A hardness values obtained from the Sauter HDA 100-1 digital hardness meter tests on the 12 samples.

Fig. 12. Shore A hardness values for the 12 samples.

Analyzing Figure 12, it can be concluded that artificial aging does not significantly affect the hardness of butt pressure welded joints of PE100 SDR11 pipes and that all the values obtained are within the range of average/soft hardness Shore A according to SR EN ISO 868, [27].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

To determine the influence of aging of pipelines used in natural gas transport and distribution on the shore A hardness and tensile behavior of butt-welded butt joints of PE100 SDR11 pipes with 125 mm nominal diameter and 11.40 mm wall thickness, 12 test samples were used in this study. The samples (9 taken from the butt-welded area) were divided into 3 groups of 4 pieces each (1 unwelded and 3 welded samples). Using the Arrhenius method, the samples in 2 groups were artificially aged by 10 and 20 years. In [22], higher tensile strength values were obtained for the welded samples than for the unwelded ones. Our study results show that the welded samples obtained higher tensile strength by 1.23-1.61%. The tensile tests for the welded sample artificially aged for 10 years (sample no. 6 in Figure 3) showed the maximum tensile strength value of 24.71 MPa.

The butt pressure welding significantly influenced the elongation at break of the non-artificially aged samples, decreasing it by 44.07-48.14%. In [24], the tensile strength improved along with increasing aging time. In our study the 10-year pipeline increased its breaking strength by 5.61-6.50% and decreased its elongation at break by 0.65-88.89%. For the same type of pipe size and 20 years artificial aging, the ultimate tensile strength increased by 2.01-6.16% and the elongation at break decreased by 6.45-45.71%.

The Shore A hardnesses obtained from the Sauter HDA 100-1 digital hardness meter tests on the 12 samples are within the range of average/soft hardnesses.

This type of pipes is used in natural gas transportation and distribution. In a future paper, research will be conducted on how the reliability of polyethylene pipes is influenced by the butt welds made during over a longer period of time along with the addition of other factors that can influence the life of the pipe.

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The Effectiveness of determining the Load-bearing Capacity of Piles based on the Results of Pile Dynamic Testing: The Case Study of Long An Province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Determining the load-bearing capacity of piles currently relies on various field experimental methods, with static pile compression loading testing and dynamic pile testing through Pile Driving Analysis (PDA) being widely accepted as reliable practices. However, the application of PDA tests faces limitations, especially in construction projects with weak soil profile while the static pile load test usually requires high testing costs. Consequently, the conventional dynamic pile testing method, checking the resistance through a number of dynamic hammer blows, is commonly utilized. Despite its prevalence, there has been limited research on the traditional dynamic pile testing method. In light of this, the present study aims to examine the traditional approach by analytical and numerical simulations. By doing so, it seeks to offer a more objective and comprehensive understanding of its effectiveness when compared to alternative methods.

Keywords-pile driving analysis; dynamic pile testing; pile bearing capacity; Plaxis software

I. INTRODUCTION

When evaluating the load-bearing capacity of piles, static pile compression loading testing emerges as the most reliable and extensively utilized method. This approach simulates the interaction between the pile and the surrounding soil, creating a critical state for the pile that encompasses ultimate skin friction and end bearing capacity. The testing procedure entails applying incremental loads and recording corresponding displacements. The ultimate bearing capacity of the pile becomes evident through the load-displacement graph constructed from these records. While notable advantages include its versatility and high reliability for various pile types, it is essential to acknowledge some significant drawbacks, such as the time-consuming nature of the testing process and the associated costs. However, assessing the load-bearing capacity of piles, especially for those with substantial lengths, inclined or submerged piles, the former presents challenges during static compression testing. The reliability of the results may be compromised in such scenarios. To address this, Pile Driving Analysis (PDA), a dynamic pile load test (PDA), capable of measuring large deformations, is employed to validate static

pile compression test results [1]. Notably, the PDA technique offers the additional advantage of detecting the integrity of a pile. This detection is crucial in situations like pile driving where deflection or damage is common. Despite these advantages, PDA accuracy hinges on the technical proficiency of experimenters, given the complexity involved in assuming initial parameters for pile and soil profile, which can be used to construct a calculation model for dynamic analysis [2]. However, the PDA method results depend heavily on the specific soil conditions at the testing location. Soil heterogeneity can make the pile quality evaluation challenging. Moreover, the PDA equipment may require a significant initial investment, while conducting the tests also demands professionalism. This can contribute to an overall increase in project costs.

Evaluating the load-bearing capacity of piles through traditional pile dynamic analysis involves assessing the residual settlement of piles under dynamic loads, such as the number of blows required for a certain displacement. This method is relatively simple and cost-effective, making it suitable for a wide range of piles [3]. The experimental principle is rooted in Newton's laws, treating the pile as a rigid body with

concentrated soil resistance at the pile tip. Following a rest period for the soil beneath the pile tip to stabilize, a pile-driving hammer, either pneumatic or diesel, imparts an impact force to the pile head. The hammer energy corresponds to the total soil resistance, leading to pile settlement and energy loss during the driving process [7]. Despite its simplicity and cost-effectiveness, this method accuracy is not optimal, prompting the need for further research to refine and enhance its precision, with the goal of reducing experimental and project expenses.

In this paper, within a case study context of a construction project which includes port, embankments, hydraulic structures, and small to medium-sized bridges with pile foundations, the practical assessment of pile load-bearing capacity compared to design requirements often hinges on the dynamic pile testing outcomes. This method is crucial for determining the appropriate pile length for general construction purposes. Recognizing this approach significance, the research focuses on the traditional dynamic pile testing method, which predicts pile load-bearing capacity based on pile driving refusal. The aim is to strengthen the theoretical foundations, and validate the dependability of computational results, aligning with the prevalent practices in the Vietnamese construction landscape.

II. PROJECT INFORMATION

Project location: The Binh Dien Fertilizer Plant is situated on the left bank of the Vam Co Dong River, downstream from the Ben Luc Bridge, in Long Dinh Commune, Can Duoc District, Long An Province.

Project scale: 3000DWT wharf, on pile foundation consisting of 126 pre-stressed concrete piles D600-C, with pile lengths ranging from 34 m to 36 m.

Fig. 1. Cross-section of the structure.

D600-C is composed of pre-stressed concrete piles with the following specifications:

- Outer diameter: $d = 0.6$ m
- Wall thickness: $t = 0.1$ m
- Pile tip cross-sectional area: $A_b = 0.283$ m²
- Circumference of the the pile: $u = 1.885$ m
- Concrete strength of the pile: $R_b = 60$ MPa

- Elastic modulus: $E_b = 28.5 \times 103$ MPa
- Maximum axial load: 414 T
- Suitable construction load: 373 T
- Crack resistance moment: $M_{cr} \geq 29$ Tm

Details of the piles before conducting dynamic testing can be seen in Table I.

TABLE I. PILE ELEVATION OF 4 TESTED PILES (m)

No.	Pile top elevation	Pile tip elevation
Pile A3 – 34 m length	+1.32	-32.68
Pile D8 – 36 m length	+2.53	-33.47
Pile F12 – 36 m length	+3.65	-32.35
Pile C17 – 36 m length	+3.70	-32.30

III. PILE LOAD-BEARING ANALYSIS

A. Load-bearing Capacity of Ailes according to the Geotechnical Criteria of the Soil

Calculations were done according to Section 7, Vietnam Standard 10304:2014. The ultimate compressive load-bearing capacity $R_{c,u}$ (kN) of a suspended or driven pile is determined by the sum of the resistance of the soil beneath the pile tip and along the pile shaft:

$$R_{c,u} = \gamma_c \left(\gamma_{cq} q_b A_b + u \sum \gamma_{cf} f_i l_i \right) \quad (1)$$

where γ_c is the working condition factor of the pile in the soil, q_b is the resistance strength of the soil beneath the pile tip, A_b is the area of the pile bearing on the soil, taken as the cross-sectional area of the pile tip, including the capped tip, u is the circumference of the cross-sectional area of the pile shaft, f_i is the average resistance strength of the i^{th} soil layer along the pile shaft, l_i is the length of the pile segment within the i^{th} soil layer, and γ_{cq} and γ_{cf} are the working condition factors of the soil beneath the pile tip and along the pile shaft, considering the influence of the pile driving method on the soil resistance.

The allowable compressive load-bearing capacity of piles, based on the soil geotechnical criteria, with γ_k being the reliability factor regarding the soil in the high-rise pier foundation case, is dependent on the number of piles in the foundation:

$$R_{c,d} = \frac{R_{c,u}}{\gamma_k} \quad (2)$$

The results of pile load-bearing from (2) are displayed In Table II.

TABLE II. PILE LOAD-BEARING CAPACITY OF 4 TESTED PILES ACCORDING TO THE GEOTECHNICAL CRITERIA OF THE SOIL (TON)

No.	$R_{c,u}$	$R_{c,d}$
Pile A3	278.95	199.25
Pile D8	289.01	206.44
Pile F12	274.79	196.28
Pile C17	274.16	195.83

B. Load-bearing Capacity of Piles according to Standard Penetration Test (SPT)

Calculations were done according to Appendix G, Vietnam Standard 10304:2014. The ultimate compressive load-bearing capacity $R_{c,u}$ (kN) is:

$$R_{c,u} = q_b A_b + u \sum (f_{c,i} l_{c,i} + f_{s,i} l_{s,i}) \tag{3}$$

where q_b is the resistance strength of the soil beneath the pile tip, A_b is the area of the pile bearing on the soil, taken as the cross-sectional area of the pile tip, including the capped tip, u is the circumference of the cross-sectional area of the pile shaft, $f_{c,i}$ is the average resistance strength along the pile segment within the i^{th} cohesive soil layer, $l_{c,i}$ is the length of the pile segment within the i^{th} cohesive soil layer, $f_{s,i}$ is the average resistance strength along the pile segment within the i^{th} loose soil layer, and $l_{s,i}$ is the length of the pile segment within the i^{th} loose soil layer.

The allowable compressive load-bearing capacity of piles according to SPT, with FS being the Factor Safety (from 2.0 to 3.0) is:

$$R_{c,d} = \frac{R_{c,u}}{FS} \tag{4}$$

The results of pile load-bearing from (4) are displayed in Table III.

TABLE III. PILE LOAD-BEARING CAPACITY OF 4 TESTED PILES ACCORDING TO SPT (TON)

No.	$R_{c,u}$	$R_{c,d}$
Pile A3	408.64	136.21
Pile D8	486.64	162.21
Pile F12	418.72	139.57
Pile C17	406.92	135.64

C. Load-bearing Capacity of piles according to the PDA test

a) SMITH Model

The Smith model employs the finite difference method to find a solution to the stress wave equation under ultimate load. Smith model transforms the stress wave transmission equation into a system of discrete element differential equations in the pile-soil-hammer system [8].

b) CASE Model

The Case model employs the principle of stress wave transmission in a one-dimensional rod, measuring the force and particle velocity waves at the pile head. The model analyzes the wave graphs to determine the pile load-bearing capacity [9]. The Case model allows for the calculation of load-bearing capacity to be performed immediately after the experiment concludes. The calculation method does not rely on the matching of assumed calculated signal waves and measured real waves, which distinguishes it from the other two models.

c) CAPWAP Model

The CAPWAP (Case Pile Wave Analysis Program) model is also known as the signal matching method. The CAPWAP model inherits and combines the Smith and Case models based on the common principle of stress wave transmission. On this

basis, the CAPWAP model constructs both the pile model and the soil model [10, 11]. The CAPWAP model is an improved and more advanced version of the Smith model. It considers additional behaviors in the pile-soil system that the Smith model does not address. Some of them are: the propagation of dynamic resistance, the unloading and reloading process, the dynamic resistance of pile materials, the behavior of pile tips on stiff ground, and the elastic-visco-plastic behavior of the soil.

The results of the pile load-bearing from PDA test by the CAPWAP model are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV. PILE LOAD-BEARING OF 4 TESTED PILES ACCORDING TO THE PDA TEST (TON)

No.	$R_{c,u}$	$R_{c,d}$
Pile A3	265.0	189.29
Pile D8	271.2	193.71
Pile F12	266.3	190.21
Pile C17	285.5	203.93

D. Load-bearing Capacity of Piles according to Dynamic Pile Testing

The experiment is based on Newton's laws with the assumption that the pile is a rigid body and the soil resistance is concentrated at the pile tip. After a resting period, allowing the soil beneath the pile tip to return to a stable state, a pile-driving hammer is used to apply an impact force to the pile head [12, 13]. The energy of the pile-driving hammer is equal to the soil total resistance, resulting in pile residual settlement and energy loss during pile driving. The anticipated dynamic pile residual settlement calculated according to Vietnam Standard 9394:2012 is:

$$e \leq \frac{nFE_n}{\frac{kP}{M}(\frac{kP}{M} + nF)} \times \frac{Q_T + \varepsilon^2(q + q_1)}{Q_T + q + q_1} \tag{5}$$

where e is the residual settlement, equal to the pile settlement due to one blow of the pile-driving hammer (m), k is the soil safety factor, depending on the number of piles in the foundation, P is the calculated load-bearing capacity of the pile (T), E_n is the calculated energy of one hammer blow (T.m), Q_T is the total weight of the hammer (T), q is the weight of the pile and pile cap (T), q_1 is the weight of the pile cushion (T), M is a factor equal to 1.0 for pile driving, n is a factor equal to 150 for precast concrete piles with caps (T/m²), ε^2 is the rebound restitution coefficient, taken as 0.2 when driving precast concrete piles with caps, and F is the cross-sectional area of the pile according to the outer perimeter (m²).

The results of pile load-bearing from the Dynamic Pile Testing are shown in Table V.

TABLE V. PILE LOAD-BEARING CAPACITY OF 4 TESTED PILES ACCORDING TO THE PDA TEST (TON)

No.	$R_{c,u}$	$R_{c,d}$
Pile A3	170.40	121.71
Pile D8	194.16	138.68
Pile F12	185.40	132.43
Pile C17	273.94	195.67

E. Load-bearing Capacity of Piles according to the Finite Element Method (Plaxis software)

1) Subsoil Model

The Mohr–Coulomb model approximately simulates the stress–strain relationship of the soil based on the elastic–plastic law [4]. The Hardening Soil model simulates the stress–strain relationship of the soil using a Hyperbolic curve reached from the elastoplastic theory instead of the elastic theory. Therefore, the Hardening Soil model has the capability to simulate non-reversible stress–strain behavior, making it more accurate in representing the real soil characteristics [5, 6]. Three elastic moduli, E_{50}^{ref} , E_{oed}^{ref} , E_{ur}^{ref} , were selected based on the results of triaxial CU tests and unconfined compression tests on all soil layers investigated in this study.

2) Input Data in Plaxis

The considered parameters used as input in Plaxis can be seen in Tables VI and VII.

TABLE VI. SOIL PARAMETERS IN PLAXIS

	Unit	Layer 1	Layer 2A	Layer 2B (above)	Layer 2B (below)
Type		HS	HS	HS	HS
γ_{unsat}	kN/m ³	15.2	20.4	20.5	20.5
γ_{sat}	kN/m ³	15.46	20.82	20.89	20.89
E_{50}^{ref}	kN/m ²	2700	10000	15000	23000
E_{oed}^{ref}	kN/m ²	2700	10000	15000	23000
E_{ur}^{ref}	kN/m ²	8100	30000	45000	69000
m		0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5
ν_{ur}		0.34	0.3	0.25	0.25
c	kN/m ²	12.9	14.4	14	14
ϕ	(^o)	12.15	24.7	25.7	25.7
ψ	(^o)	0	0	0	0
R_{inter}		0.6	0.7	0.8	0.8

TABLE VII. PILE PARAMETERS IN PLAXIS

Pile D600-C	Symbol	Unit	Value
Type			Elastic
Mass per meter length of the pile	w	kN/m/m	4.08
Mass moment of inertia	I	m ⁴	0.00511
Elastic modulus	E	KN/m ²	2.85E+07
Poisson's ratio	ν		0.2
Compression stiffness	E.A	KN/m	4.477E+06
Flexural stiffness	E.I	KN/m ² /m	1.455E+05

Fig. 2. Cross-section of the structure in Plaxis.

3) Calculation Model

The geometry and the calculation model of the project are shown in Figure 2.

4) Modeling Calculation Results

Figure 3 illustrates the plot of the vertical displacement of the pile head over time (Dynamic time - Uy). The results of the pile displacement (deflection), as the oscillation gradually diminishes until stability is reached, can be observed.

Fig. 3. Graph of vertical displacement at the head of pile D8 (Uy) over time.

The output outcomes of the maximum axial force appearing in the pile is the sum of the reactions from the soil below the pile tip acting on the pile and the friction along the perimeter of the pile that is mobilized to the maximum during the pile subjection to dynamic loading. The results from the envelope of bending moment diagram contribute to structural design optimization, allowing for adjustments in materials, dimensions, or other parameters to meet the specific criteria (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Axial forces and bending moments at pile D8.

TABLE VIII. PILE LOAD-BEARING CAPACITY OF 4 TESTED PILES ACCORDING TO MODELING (TON)

No.	$R_{c,u}$	$R_{c,d}$
Pile A3	197	140.71
Pile D8	199	142.14
Pile F12	201	143.57
Pile C17	199	142.14

IV. PILE LOAD-BEARING COMPARISON

In this segment, the comparison of the ultimate bearing capacity and the allowable load-bearing capacity of the piles among various approaches is illustrated in Figures 5 and 6.

Fig. 5. Comparison of pile ultimate bearing capacity results.

Fig. 6. Comparison of allowable pile load-bearing capacity results.

Figure 5 reveals that the ultimate bearing capacity, which is predicted based on the SPT values, consistently yields notably higher values, than the other methods, with the difference reaching 100 tons. However, Figure 6 indicates less variability in the allowable load across the techniques, with a maximum difference of approximately 50 tons. This discrepancy may be attributed to the factor of safety applied in accordance with Vietnamese standards. Engineers should exercise caution when employing each method for bearing capacity determination within the context of these standards. The traditional dynamic approach consistently shows lower ultimate bearing capacity values from the other techniques, as depicted in Figure 5. Notably, in the case of pile C17, the dynamic approach records a higher bearing capacity of 273.94 tons compared to an average of around 200 tons for piles A3, D8, and F12. Interestingly, the results from numerical simulation with Plaxis align with the traditional dynamic approach outcomes. Figures 5 and 6 also highlight a noteworthy agreement between the bearing capacity as determined by soil characteristics and PDA. The consistent values suggest that PDA serves as a reliable method for foreseeing pile responses. Particularly, the

allowable load in Figure 6 demonstrates that the two techniques, utilizing soil characteristics and PDA, yield higher values than the other approaches.

V. CONCLUSION

This study undertook a thorough investigation into the bearing capacity and allowable loading of piles, utilizing five distinct approaches, with a particular emphasis on the economical and time-efficient traditional dynamic approach. The key findings and implications of this study are:

- **Traditional Dynamic Approach Reliability:** The results of ultimate bearing capacity and allowable load obtained through the traditional dynamic approach exhibit agreement with the numerical simulation in Plaxis, highlighting its reliability. However, variations, notably in the case of pile C17, indicate certain limitations that engineers should consider in practical applications.
- **PDA and Soil Characteristics:** The consistently demonstrated validity of the results from PDS and soil characteristic approaches establishes PDA as a reliable method for determining pile responses. Additionally, the allowable load predictions from these approaches consistently surpass those of the other methods.
- **SPT Approach Considerations:** While the bearing capacity predicted from the SPT approach exhibited the highest values, the allowable load predictions demonstrate smaller values, potentially influenced by the safety factor determined by Vietnamese standards. Caution is recommended in practical applications.
- **Future Research Directions:** To enhance the understanding of field-measured pile driving deflection in various structural scenarios, using pile foundation methods, extensive research is recommended. Future work should encompass diverse geological and subsurface conditions, including medium sand, coarse sand, stiff clay, semi-stiff clay, among others. Such investigations will contribute to refining and advancing current practices in the field.

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Automated Skin Cancer Detection and Classification using Cat Swarm Optimization with a Deep Learning Model

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ABSTRACT

The application of Computer Vision (CV) and image processing in the medical sector is of great significance, especially in the recognition of skin cancer using dermoscopic images. Dermoscopy denotes a non-invasive imaging system that offers clear visuals of skin cancers, allowing dermatologists to analyze and identify various features crucial for lesion assessment. Over the past few years, there has been an increasing fascination with Deep Learning (DL) applications for skin cancer recognition, with a particular focus on the impressive results achieved by Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). DL approaches, predominantly CNNs, have exhibited immense potential in automating the classification and detection of skin cancers. This study presents an Automated Skin Cancer Detection and Classification method using Cat Swarm Optimization with Deep Learning (ASCDC-CSODL). The main objective of the ASCDC-CSODL method is to enforce the DL model to recognize and classify skin tumors on dermoscopic images. In ASCDC-CSODL, Bilateral Filtering (BF) is applied for noise elimination and U-Net is employed for the segmentation process. Moreover, the ASCDC-CSODL method exploits MobileNet for the feature extraction process. The Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) approach is used for the classification of skin cancer. Finally, the CSO algorithm alters the hyperparameter values of GRU. A wide-ranging simulation was performed to evaluate the performance of the ASCDC-CSODL model, demonstrating the significantly improved results of the ASCDC-CSODL model over other approaches.

Keywords-skin cancer; dermoscopic images; deep learning; cat swarm optimization; computer-aided diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Today, skin cancer is an increasingly common type of cancer. There are several types of skin carcinoma [1]. Melanoma is the most prevalent cancer in both males and females [2]. As the initial indicators of skin cancer may not always be visible, diagnostic assessments typically rely on the expertise of dermatologist specialists. For untrained physicians, an automatic diagnosis system is a crucial tool for a highly accurate diagnosis [3]. Apart from that, the diagnosis of skin carcinoma with the naked eye is rarely generalizable and extremely subjective. Therefore, there is a need to improve automated classification systems to be even more accurate, cost-effective, and faster [4]. Furthermore, the implementation of such automatic diagnostic systems can efficiently reduce mortality from skin cancers and help medical systems and patients [5].

Several medical professionals use Artificial Intelligence (AI) for clinical diagnoses to improve diagnosis decision-

making processes [6]. However, the currently available AI research has neglected existing evidence of development, accurate evaluation, and sufficient reports of predictive errors in such fields. Computer-aided diagnosis techniques could rapidly, reliably, and regularly diagnose different diseases [7]. Computer-aided diagnosis provides options for accurate and low-cost detection or protection from developed tumors. Individual organ diseases are usually diagnosed using various imaging techniques, such as MRI, X-rays, and PET [8]. Initially, methods such as clinical screening, dermoscopy image analysis, Computed Tomography (CT), etc., are used to visually diagnose skin lesions. Dermatologists with few skills have exhibited minimal accuracy in the diagnosis of skin lesions [9]. The techniques for practitioners to analyze and evaluate lesion images are complex, error-prone, time-consuming, and subjective [10]. The use of Machine Learning (ML) has offered considerable developments in prediction systems and computer-aided diagnosis for detecting skin cancer.

This study presents an Automated Skin Cancer Detection and Classification method using Cat Swarm Optimization with Deep Learning (ASDC-SCODL). The main objective of ASCDC-SCODL is to apply DL on dermoscopic images to recognize and classify skin tumors. This method uses Bilateral Filtering (BF) for the noise elimination process and U-Net for the segmentation process. Moreover, the ASCDC-SCODL method exploits MobileNet for the feature extraction process. The classification of skin cancer is performed using a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), and the CSO algorithm adjusts the hyperparameter values of the GRU. A wide-ranging simulation was performed to evaluate the performance of the proposed ASCDC-SCODL method.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In [11], a lightweight skin carcinoma detection technique was presented, depending on the principle of fine-grained categorization and using two categories of training models, negative and positive model sets, as input into the feature extraction segment (lightweight CNNs). In [12], an innovative DL-based architecture was proposed for the multi-categorization of skin carcinoma categories (basal cell cancer, benign keratosis, melanocytic nevi, and melanoma). This SCDNet integrated VGG16 with CNNs to classify many types of skin cancer. In [13], a DNN was used with fine-tuning training and enhanced learning performance on dermoscopic images to detect skin cancer. Fine-tuning and Transfer Learning (TL) were implemented for faster training on restricted trained datasets. In [14], the Intelligent Multi-Level Thresholding with DL (IMLT-DL) method was proposed, which relied on skin cancer segmentation and classification models using dermoscopic images. This method combined inpainting and top-hat filtering methods for the preprocessing of dermoscopic images. In addition, MFOs with multilevel Kapur thresholds rely on segmentation processes that are included in identifying diseased areas. Finally, the classifier used the Gradient Boosting Tree (GBT) technique.

In [15], a DCNN-based method was presented to classify skin carcinoma types with greater accuracy. An EfficientNet framework based on TL models was applied, which learned highly complicated and fine-grained models from skin cancer images by automatic scaling width, resolution, and depth of networks. In [16], an innovative CNN scheme was developed based on atrous convolutions for automated skin lesion segmentation. This design relies on the idea of dilated or atrous convolution, which is efficient for semantic segmentation. The DNN was implemented from scratch using many building blocks that contained leakyReLU, batch normalization, and convolutional layers, along with fine-tuned hyperparameters to provide enhanced performance. In [17], an ensemble method was proposed that used Swin-Transformer and EfficientNetV2S to detect the initial focal region of skin cancer, having the benefit of identifying dark regions in the images. In [18], a Fractal Neural Network-Based Galactic Swarm Optimization (FNN-GSO) was proposed, involving four components and using adaptive watershed segmentation. Then, the DWT-GLCM and FNN-GSO approaches were used for feature extraction and classification.

In [19], the Sand CSO with Deep Transfer Learning Method (SCSODTL-SCC) was proposed, where segmentation and classification processes used a hybrid Deep Belief Network (DBN) model incorporating U2Net and NASNetLarge-based feature extractors, while the SCSO model was used for the tuning process. In [20], a model was presented that used auxiliary function smoothing, built with a prevalent local minimizer, and smoothed using Bezier curves to determine threshold values in images related to melanoma skin cancer. In [21], an automated diagnostic system was introduced using a support vector machine, which was an improved iteration of the fluid search optimization approach rooted in chaos theory, contributing to a faster convergence speed. In [22], the Cat Swarm-Intelligent Generative RNN (CS-IGRNN) approach was presented, which employed the Weiner Filter (WF) for image preprocessing. The features were extracted through Gabor Filter Bank (GFB) processing, and the use of CS-IGRNN was suggested as a prospective solution for the categorization of cancer images.

Despite the advances in skin cancer detection techniques, several drawbacks are evident in existing methodologies. Some methods exhibit computational complexity due to the integration of multiple algorithms, potentially impacting real-time processing efficiency and resource utilization. Additionally, challenges persist in achieving a balance between sensitivity and specificity, which are crucial for minimizing false positives or negatives in skin cancer diagnoses. Furthermore, the reliance on extensive computational resources and large datasets for training can pose practical challenges, especially in resource-constrained medical settings.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

This study designed an ASCDC-SCODL approach to apply DL on dermoscopic images to classify and recognize skin cancer. In ASCDC-SCODL, the BF method is used for the noise elimination process and U-Net is employed for the segmentation process. Additionally, the proposed method uses MobileNet for feature extraction. Also, the classification of skin tumors is performed using the GRU technique. Finally, CSO adjusts the hyperparameter values of the GRU. Figure 1 illustrates the workflow of the proposed ASCDC-SCODL method.

A. Image Preprocessing

The BF technique was used to preprocess the input images. This method decreases noise but maintains the fine and edge details of the images [23]. It accomplishes this by taking into account either spatial distance or intensity similarity among pixels. An important stage of the BF approach is:

- Determine a window or kernel of a certain size.
- For the overall image pixels, compute the weighted average of its nearby pixels depending on either spatial distance or intensity similarity.
- The weights can be defined by a spatial Gaussian function and an intensity Gaussian function. The spatial Gaussian function ensures that nearby pixels take a superior weight,

and the intensity Gaussian function ensures that pixels with the same intensity take a superior weight.

Fig. 1. Workflow of the ASCDC-CSODL approach.

B. Image Segmentation

The U-Net approach was used to segment the dermoscopic images. U-Net is the most widely used segmentation model, depending on the encoder-decoder neural structure and the use of skip connections [24]. This method receives an image as input during encoding, exploits more than one layer of convolution, ReLU activation, max-pooling, and encompasses the data into hidden space. The only difference between the plain encoder-decoder and the U-Net method is the usage of skip connections to transmit the data in the higher-resolution layer of encoded to decoded, which might assist in better capturing smaller details. CNURject demonstrates the overall framework of U-Net. U-Net exploits the following loss function to train like other neural segmentation models:

$$\mathcal{L}_{U_{net}} = \sum_{x \in \Omega} \omega(x) \log(p_{\ell(x)}(x)) \quad (1)$$

where $\ell: \Omega \rightarrow \{1, \dots, K\}$, $\Omega \subset \mathbb{Z}^2$, and K indicates the overall amount of class labels. While applying the binary cross entropy, $K = 2$. Furthermore, the softmax is described as $p_k(x) = \exp(a_k(x)) / \sum_{k'=1}^K \exp(a_{k'}(x))$, where $a_k(x)$ denotes the activation in the feature channel K .

Furthermore, in a network that has different convolution layers, the primary weight considerably affects the achievement. Consequently, roughly the unit variance of the primary weight of the network feature map was carried out effectively. With the ReLU and U-Net convolutional layers, employing a Gaussian distribution with SD of $\sqrt{2/N}$ is the best solution, where N denotes the number of nodes received from a single neuron.

C. Feature Extraction

The MobileNet architecture was used for feature extraction. It is a shallow DNN technique that is optimal for decreasing computational cost and time [25]. MobileNet alternates depth-wise convolution with standard convolutions to minimize model processing and size. Employing a factorizing system

termed depthwise convolutional, a normal convolution was separated into 2 convolutions: point-wise and depth-wise. A 1×1 -dimensional convolution is point-wise. Point-wise convolution tries to join, whereas depth-wise tries to filter. The procedure of depth-wise distinguishable convolutions is the outcome of more depth-wise and point-wise convolutions. In addition to the upper layer, the structure of MobileNet contained separable convolutions.

D. Image Classification using Optimal GRU Model

The GRU model was used to effectively recognize and classify skin tumors. The GRU framework has adaptive memory and forgets the hidden unit [26]. The reset gate was computed as:

$$r_j = \sigma([W_r x]_j + [u_r h_{<f-1>}]_j) \quad (2)$$

where σ refers to the activation function of the logistic sigmoid, $[*]_j$ represents the j^{th} module of the vector, x denotes the input, and h_{t-1} denotes the preceding moment to allow the status. The matrices W_r and U_r are identified weighted matrices. The upgrade gate was computed by:

$$z_j = \sigma([W_z x]_j + [u_z h_{<t-1>}]_j) \quad (3)$$

where h_j demonstrates the target cell state vector that was measured by:

$$h_j^{<t>} = z_j \odot h_j^{<t-1>} + (1 - z_j) \odot h_j^{<t>} \quad (4)$$

$$h_{j<t>} = \tanh([Wx]_j + [U(\odot h_{(t-1)})]_j) \quad (5)$$

where \odot stands for multiplication performed on a per-element basis. Finally, the hyperparameter selection of the GRU model was performed by the CSO algorithm. CSO is established dependent on the cat's performance. The CSO contains 2 sub-modes: seeking and tracing [27].

1) Seeking Mode

During the SCO procedure, the seeking mode was projected to model the cat in resting time and then alertly search nearby places for its next moves. Four important aspects can be executed in the seeking mode: Count of Dimension to Change (CDC), Seeking Range of the selected Dimension (SRD), Seeking Memory Pool (SMP), and Self-Position Consideration (SPC). SMP determines the seeking memory size of all cats that represent any point sorted by a cat. SRD denotes the mutative ratio to the elected dimension. Once the dimension is chosen for mutation, the difference between new and old values cannot be outside the range determined by SRD. CDC means that several dimensions are different. Each factor plays a vital role in this mode. SPC is a Boolean value and represents if the point where the cat was previously standing is going to be the best Candidate Point (CP) to move to. SPC could not stimulate the SMP value. The seeking mode is explained as follows:

- Create j copies of the current location of cat_k , where $j = SMP$. When SPC is true, consider $(SMP-1)$, and then keep the current position as most candidates.

- For all the copies, based on *CDC*, arbitrarily select positive or negative *SRD* percent of the existing values and exchange them with old ones.
- Compute the value of fitness (*FS*) of every *CP*.
- If every *FS* could not accurately be equivalent, compute the choosing probability of all the *CPs* based on (6). Otherwise, set every electing probability of all the *CPs* that are equal to 1.
- Arbitrarily choose the point to move in the *CPs*, and exchange the location of cat_k :

$$P_i = \frac{|FS_i - FS_b|}{FS_{max} - FS_{min}}, \text{ where } 0 < i < j \quad (6)$$

The Fitness Function's (*FF*) purpose is to determine the minimal outcome, assume $FS_b = FS_{max}$, else, $FS_b = FS_{min}$.

2) *Tracing Mode*

Tracing mode methods the occurrence of cats from tracing goals. If a cat switches to the tracing mode, it starts moving based on the individual velocities of all the dimensions. The tracing mode is performed as:

- Upgrade the velocity to all the dimensions $v_{k,d}(z)$ for cat_k at the present iteration based on:

$$v_{k,d}(z) = v_{k,d}(z - 1) + r_1 \cdot c_1 \cdot [x_{best,d}(z - 1) - x_{k,d}(z - 1)], d = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (7)$$

- Verify if the velocity is in the maximal velocity range. When the novel velocity is out of range, it can be adjusted to the range.
- Upgrade the location of cat_k based on:

$$x_{k,d}(z) = x_{k,d}(z - 1) + v_{k,d}(z) \quad (8)$$

where $x_{best,d}(z-1)$ depicts the cat position that takes an optimal value of fitness at the prior iteration, and $x_{k,d}(z-1)$ denotes the location of cat_k . In the preceding iteration, c_1, r_1 indicate the constant and the arbitrary value within [0, 1]. *CSO* illustrates an *FF* for higher classifier outcomes. It controls a positive numeral to exemplify the good solution of candidate performance. The error rate of the minimized classifier can be regarded as a *FF*:

$$fitness(x_i) = \frac{\text{No. of misclassified instances}}{\text{Total No. of instances}} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

IV. PERFORMANCE VALIDATION

The proposed ASCDC-CSODL method was evaluated on the ISIC2017 and HAM10000 datasets. Figure 2 shows some sample images. The dataset contains 2000 samples under 3 classes. The proposed method was simulated using Python 3.6.5 on an i5-8600K, GeForce 1050Ti 4GB, 250GB SSD, 1TB HDD, and 16GB RAM PC. The parameter setup was: learning rate: 0.01, activation: ReLU, epoch count: 50, dropout: 0.5, and batch size: 5.

ASCDC-CSODL was compared with previous methods, and Figure 3 shows the comparison results in the ISIC2017 dataset [28]. The NB, MSVM, KELM, MobileNet, and DenseNet169 methods achieved poor results. The MAFCNN-

SCD method has revealed substantial performance with $accu_y, sens_y, spec_y,$ and F_{score} of 92.22, 77.07, 88.67, and 83.05%, respectively, while the proposed ASCDC-CSODL method showed even better results with $accu_y, sens_y, spec_y,$ and F_{score} of 97.44, 93.42, 97.01, and 94.63%, respectively.

Fig. 2. Sample images.

Fig. 3. Relative output of ASCDC-CSODL and other methods in the ISIC2017 dataset.

Fig. 4. Relative output of the ASCDC-CSODL and other methods in the HAM10000 dataset.

Figure 4 shows a comparison of ASCDC-CSODL with MAFCNN-SCD, NB, MSVM, KELM, MobileNet, and DenseNet169 methods in the HAM10000 dataset. The results show that NB, MSVM, KELM, MobileNet, and DenseNet169 reported comparably poor performance. The MAFCNN-SCD method has exposed substantial outputs with $accu_y$, $sens_y$, $spec_y$, and F_{score} of 92.22, 77.07, 88.67, and 80.05, respectively. ASCDC-CSODL provided the best results with $accu_y$, $sens_y$, $spec_y$, and F_{score} of 98.48, 78.06, 98.45, and 82.18%, respectively. Therefore, the ASCDC-CSODL method can be used effectively for skin cancer detection and classification purposes.

V. CONCLUSION

This study introduced the ASCDC-CSODL approach, which used a DL model to classify and recognize skin cancer in dermoscopy images. In this approach, the noise elimination process involved the application of the BF method, the segmentation process was carried out using U-Net, and feature extraction was performed using MobileNet. Skin tumor classification was performed through GRU, with hyperparameter values adjusted by the CSO technique. The effectiveness of the ASCDC-CSODL approach was validated through simulations, exhibiting improved results of 97.44% and 98.48% in two datasets over other approaches. Future research could focus on enhancing the ASCDC-CSODL approach by addressing its computational complexity and refining its ability to generalize across diverse skin conditions. Furthermore, exploring the integration of additional advanced image processing or DL techniques may contribute to overcoming current limitations and improving overall performance.

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Research and Development of a Traffic Sign Recognition Module in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Automatic traffic sign recognition is essential in researching and developing driver assistance systems and autonomous vehicles. This paper presents the research and development of an automated traffic sign recognition module in Vietnam. The recognition model is developed based on the deep learning model YOLOv5 and incorporates architectural modifications to reduce computational complexity, increase inference speed, and meet real-time requirements for embedded system applications. The model is trained using a custom dataset collected by the research team from real-world street environments in Vietnam, encompassing diverse locations, times, and weather conditions. The trained recognition model is deployed on the Jetson embedded system, yielding high-quality recognition results and meeting real-time recognition needs.

Keywords-deep learning; traffic sign recognition; YOLOv5; embedded system; image processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Researching and developing traffic sign recognition is fundamental in developing driver assistance and autonomous systems. The information obtained from traffic sign recognition can aid drivers in reacting correctly to traffic conditions, reduce the risk of accidents, and improve overall driving safety. Nonetheless, developing a traffic sign recognition module is often faced with two primary challenges: customized traffic sign datasets and the trade-off between accuracy and processing speed on embedded systems. Firstly, traffic signs vary in structure and shape in each country and region, which poses difficulties when applying a pre-existing traffic sign recognition system from one country to another. A few research groups in Vietnam have conducted studies and solutions for traffic sign recognition based on the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark (GTSRB) dataset [1]. However, the signs in this dataset differ significantly in terms of shape, color, and type when compared to the Vietnamese

traffic signs. Moreover, since this dataset has been preprocessed and had its background removed, applying the model to real-world street scenarios results in lower recognition accuracy. Secondly, the trade-off between accuracy and processing speed on embedded systems is another crucial factor in the research and development of traffic sign recognition modules. Studies on traffic sign recognition typically focus on detecting regions with traffic signs and extracting distinguishing features represented by sign patterns [2, 3]. The current methods can be divided into two main groups: traditional and deep learning-based. Standard algorithms are often built based on color and shape information extracted from sample images, followed by segmenting and labeling signs through pattern classification [4]. Traditional methods yield lower accuracy due to variations in traffic signs, environmental factors, lighting conditions, image angles, and partially occluded signs. However, they offer fast processing speeds due to their low computational complexity. Recently,

with the advancement of computational hardware, research on traffic sign recognition systems has been built using object recognition algorithms based on deep learning models with multilayer neural networks for feature extraction and learning [5]. Nonetheless, most Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have millions of parameters, and they demand significant resources, memory, and computational costs, which pose challenges related to the overall system performance, particularly real-time application requirements.

Considering the aforementioned challenges, it becomes evident that researching and developing a real-time traffic sign recognition module explicitly designed for Vietnam is necessary and highly practical.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Traffic Sign Recognition Model

Deep learning-based object recognition algorithms can be divided into two main types: single-stage object recognition algorithms and two-stage object recognition algorithms. Single-stage algorithms, such as YOLO [6, 7] and Single Shot Multibox Detector [8], can extract features from the network for immediate classification, recognition, and object localization. On the other hand, two-stage detection methods are built on the proposal region principle, where regions of interest are proposed and then classified and refined. R-CNN [9], Fast R-CNN [10], and Faster R-CNN [11] are representative algorithms in this group that rely on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models.

Single-stage recognition models based on YOLO have speed and processing efficiency advantages compared to two-stage recognition models like R-CNN and its variants. This makes them suitable for deployment on embedded systems. YOLOv5 [12] consists of three main components: backbone, neck, and head. The backbone serves as the foundation of the model architecture and is responsible for extracting essential features from the input images. It uses the CSPDarkNet53 architecture, which consists of consecutive convolutional layers capable of extracting features at different scales. The neck connects the backbone and the head, processing and transmitting the extracted features from the backbone to the head. The neck utilizes PANet (Pyramid Attention Network) and FPN (Feature Pyramid Network) architectures, which play a role in fine-tuning object detection accuracy. The head is the final component responsible for object recognition based on the extracted features. Some studies have successfully used Yolo deep learning models to solve real-time application problems, such as smoke detection for trajectory planning and navigation of a mobile robot [13] and recognition of road surface anomalies [14].

Two training models, YOLOv5n (nano) and YOLOv5s (small), have been chosen to meet the deployment requirements on embedded systems. Additionally, the CSPDarkNet network architecture in the backbone of the YOLOv5 model is replaced with the MobileNet [15] network to reduce computational complexity and increase computational speed on embedded systems. Based on the training and inference speed results, the recognition models will be considered and selected for application on embedded systems.

B. A Dataset of Vietnamese Traffic signs

The dataset used to train the model was meticulously curated to encompass 16 essential traffic signs frequently encountered while driving, as depicted in Figure 1. Some signs share similarities in color and shape. It is imperative to note that if the model is not performing optimally during training, it may incorrectly identify these similar sign pairs. Therefore, besides selecting the appropriate model and training parameters, the quality of the data source for the sign is also a crucial factor. Data from multiple sources were gathered, taking into account several locations, times, weather conditions, and sign angles.

Fig. 1. Vietnamese traffic signs considered in this study.

In order to ensure a diverse range of data sources, we collected information from various devices, including cameras, phones, and dash cams installed on cars and motorbikes traveling on different routes across various provinces and cities throughout Vietnam. The collection of traffic sign samples took place at different times of day and in varying weather conditions. Data augmentation algorithms were applied to address potential imbalances within the dataset that adjust the detector's brightness, dimming, and angle. Additionally, the data were enhanced by superimposing signs onto realistic street scene backgrounds. We also incorporated other traffic sign images from the Vietnamese road traffic sign set into the training set to help the model differentiate between easily confused signs, ultimately improving the quality of the training model.

Fig. 2. The custom dataset.

The data set was split into two sets: a training set accounting for 80% of the images (24896 images) and a test set accounting for the remaining 20% (6224 images).

C. Recognition Model Deployment on the Embedded System

The advanced traffic sign recognition model was successfully implemented on NVIDIA's powerful Jetson NX (8GB) embedded system. The Jetson NX has a GPU of 48 tensor cores, providing an AI computing capacity of 21 TOPS. The trained model was optimized using TensorRT to further accelerate its inference on embedded systems. Adjusting the accuracy from FP32 to FP16 greatly reduces the number of model calculations without sacrificing precision. This precision

correction streamlines the computation process and eliminates the need to re-calibrate the model after training and optimization. The optimized model was deployed on Jetson and developed into a module with camera equipment and a display screen (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Schematic of the traffic sign recognition module.

III. TRAINING, EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS, AND DISCUSSION

A. Training Result

When assessing the effectiveness of a trained model, several key metrics were considered, such as IoU (Intersection over Union), Precision, Recall, and Mean Average Precision. IoU denotes the proportion of the predicted area that intersects with the actual object image area. Precision represents the ratio of True Positive (TP) predictions to the total number of positive predictions made by the model, encompassing both true and False Positives (FP). The model's mean accuracy (mAP) is computed across all confidence thresholds. However, only mAP 0.5:0.95 derived from IoU ranging from 0.5 to 0.95 significantly contributes to evaluating the prediction model.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{(FP+TP)} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{(FN+TP)} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N AP_i \quad (3)$$

The training model was run on a Core (TM) i7-12700F 2.10 GHz computer with 32 GB RAM and NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070 Ti GPU, CUDA 11.7. The models were trained for 100 epochs. The training process results are presented in Figure 3 and Table I. The training results indicate that the backbone correction model using MobileNet has more parameters than the original model, but has better computational performance due to its reduced complexity. The identification accuracy is proportional to the model's complexity. However, the difference in accuracy between the models is not significant.

The YOLOv5n model (MobileNet) has a computational performance of 3.1 GFLOPs for 91.8% mAP_{0.5:0.95}. The YOLOv5s (origin) model has a computational performance of 16.1 GFLOPs for 93.7% mAP_{0.5:0.95}.

In addition to the previously mentioned evaluation metrics, we should consider the energy consumption required for training when creating modules, particularly for applications with limited energy resources. As illustrated in Figure 5, the

energy consumed by the GPU during model training is directly proportional to its complexity. Out of the four models tested, the YOLOv5n model (MobileNet) exhibited the lowest energy consumption during exercise, averaging 60 Wh. On the other hand, the YOLOv5s (origin) model consumed the highest amount of energy (averaging more than 70 Wh) and took longer to train.

Fig. 4. Training results. (a) Precision, (b) mAP, (c) Recall.

TABLE I. TRAINING RESULTS

Model	Layers	Parameters	GFLOPs	mAP 0.5:0.95	Recall
YOLOv5n	214	1785565	4.3	0.927	0.999
YOLOv5n (MobileNet)	287	2156253	3.1	0.918	0.999
YOLOv5s	214	7062781	16.1	0.937	0.999
YOLOv5s (MobileNet)	287	4667901	7.4	0.925	0.998

The models were optimized using TensorRT and were deployed on Jetson NX. The research team conducted speed tests on an embedded system using videos from dashcams with resolutions of 1920×1080 and 1280×720. The inference process involves three main steps: frame pre-processing, prediction, and duplicate prediction removal algorithm (NMS). The frame pre-processing task involves separating frames from

the video and resizing them to 640×640 to match the prediction model. The preprocessed frames were then passed into the training model for prediction. Finally, a duplicate removal algorithm was applied to remove any duplicate findings. Table II provides the inference speed of the proposed recognition models.

Fig. 5. GPU power consumption during training.

TABLE II. SPEED TRAINING RESULTS

Model	Preprocessing (ms)	Prediction	NMS (ms)
YOLOv5n	2	14.2	5.6
YOLOv5n (MobileNet)	2	13.6	4.9
YOLOv5s	2	17.3	5.2
YOLOv5s (MobileNet)	2	15.3	4.9

According to the experimental findings, it is clear that the MobileNet backbone correction model offers quicker prediction results compared to the corresponding models of YOLOv5s and YOLOv5n. The sign recognition results are notably impressive, particularly when the weather conditions are favorable. Furthermore, the model performs exceptionally well even in scenarios where the signs are captured from tight angles or are partially obscured, as demonstrated in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Traffic sign recognition results under normal conditions.

Therefore, recognition models are not always equally effective under all lighting conditions. It is essential to consider the type of lighting that will be present in the environment where the recognition model will be utilized. The findings of this study highlight the importance of carefully selecting and testing recognition models in various lighting conditions to ensure optimal performance and accuracy.

The effectiveness of recognition models can vary under certain lighting conditions, particularly those in a low-light environment. In Figure 7, we can see that despite the poor

lighting conditions, the YOLOv5s, YOLOv5n, and YOLOv5s (MobileNet) models correctly identified the target. However, it is worth noting that in this particular instance, the YOLOv5n (MobileNet) model failed to recognize the target sign.

Fig. 7. Results of sign recognition in low light conditions.

Upon analyzing Figure 9(b), it is evident that the complexity of the sign recognition escalates with small size and varying surrounding color, e.g. the lights of vehicles on the road at night. In this scenario, only the YOLOv5s model can accurately detect signs that prohibit driving in the opposite direction. The precision of the model corresponds to its level of intricacy during training, which is apparent from the results.

B. Experimental Results on Streets

Through road experiments, it was noted that the module possesses a remarkable ability to detect traffic signs, even with the camera positioned behind a car's windshield (Figure 8). Upon establishing a recognition model with a prediction threshold of 0.5, the outcomes demonstrate that the module can efficiently and accurately identify signs from an average distance under 30 m (Figure 9). The YOLOv5s (original) model has an impressive average FPS (Frames Per Second) processing speed of 54, while the YOLOv5n (MobileNet) model offers an impressive processing speed of 70 FPS. These models provide accurate recognition rates and are highly suitable for real-time deployment. Additionally, users can switch between the two models during deployment based on their accuracy and recognition speed requirements, providing greater flexibility.

Fig. 8. The module set on a car.

Fig. 9. Experimenting on real conditions.

IV. CONCLUSION

The current study aimed to develop an automatic identification method for common traffic signs in Vietnam. Detection models were created based on YOLOv5, with a modified backbone using the MobileNet model to reduce the amount of computation and speed up the inference model to respond to real-time requirements.

To train the models, a diverse dataset was used, collected from various sources under varying conditions (location, weather, lighting, and shooting angles). Data augmentation techniques were employed to prevent data imbalance, which aided in improving the models' identification ability and prediction accuracy. After training, the modified models gave relatively good results, i.e. mAP 0.918 (Yolov5n+MobileNet model) and mAP 0.925 (Yolov5s+MobileNet).

After training, the optimized model was deployed on the Jetson NX embedded system. The results from actual tests conducted on the streets of Hanoi demonstrated that the module can recognize traffic signs accurately and reliably. The module can detect traffic signs in normal weather conditions and low light conditions at a distance and with a high FPS rate. The module is suitable for real-time deployment.

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The Innovative Role of Process Mining in building Face Re-identification Trajectory

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ABSTRACT

Face recognition and tracking technology have witnessed significant advancements during the recent decades. These advancements include improved accuracy and speed in identifying and tracking individuals, as well as the ability to recognize faces in various scale and lighting conditions. Leveraging the potential of face recognition and tracking, this article explores the integration of process mining techniques to discover and visualize face's appearing trajectories in crowd scenarios, aiming to enhance crowd security, surveillance, and personal identification. Notably, existing face recognition tools typically focus on bounding box localization, neglecting the utilization of face coordinates to construct trajectory models upon face re-identification. In this paper, full system architecture for building a trajectory model of re-identified faces in a crowd is proposed. This approach significantly helped in building a large database of visitor faces, and the proposed trajectory model resulted in a high rate of true positive face re-identification.

Keywords-process mining; face recognition; face detection; crowd management; surveillance; smart city; tracking

I. INTRODUCTION

Face recognition and tracking technology [1] has seen significant advancements in recent years. These advancements include improved accuracy and speed in identifying and tracking individuals, as well as the ability to recognize faces in various scale and lighting conditions. Detecting faces in crowd is growing rapidly [2]. Authors in [3] highlighted the state of arts techniques that are developed for identifying and verifying faces on large scale events. Face recognition and tracking technology have revolutionized the way we pinpoint and monitor individuals. By harnessing its power, we can now unlock new possibilities in crowd security, surveillance, and personal identification. In this article, we contribute to face recognition and tracking research, by exploring the potential use of process mining for discovering and visualizing trajectory of faces in crowd. Through the latter processes and in conjunction with face recognition techniques it may be possible for crowd behavior to be controlled. To the best of our knowledge, face recognition tools mostly rely on labeling faces by localizing box boundaries of identified faces without further utilization of face coordinates on constructing a trajectory model when a face is re-identified. This work demonstrates the feasibility of process mining principles to model face presence in crowd.

Previous research that tried to address the issue of tracking re-identified faces mostly used active bounding boxes and associated faces with random numbers for single events [4]. Some researchers have used geo-fences information to track faces that appeared in different locations in a specific event [5].

Our proposed approach aims to provide a retrospective graph-based model which shows face appearance detected in several events. The model produced is a lightweight and scalable model derived from the construction process using a textual event log.

The real-world applications of face detection and recognition are needed in an unconstrained environment which generates low resolution image quality. Several research works have addressed this issue. The work presented in [6] was one of the first research attempts that highlighted the challenges of detecting faces in such an environment. Therefore, the large database Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW), was built for model training purposes. Generally, face recognition technology utilizes algorithms to analyze and single out unique facial features of individuals. It works by capturing an image or video of a person's face and comparing it to a database of known faces. The technology can recognize specific facial characteristics namely the distance between the eyes, the nose shape, and the face contour. This information is then used to create a unique facial template for everyone, allowing for accurate identification and tracking [1].

A. General Approach of Face Recognition

A modern face recognition pipeline as suggested by [7, 8] consists of 4 common stages: Detection, Alignment, Representation, and Verification

- The Detection stage aims to localize the key landmarks of a face such as eyes, nose and mouth usually using bounding box of the detected face area.

- Alignment: The detected faces are horizontally aligned, getting prepared for the next stage. Other image pre-processing techniques such as normalization can be included in the alignment stage as well.
- Representation stage generates a vector representation or feature embeddings for each face. The Representation length depends on the technique used.
- Verification stage compares a pair of faces to test if they match.

B. Crowd Management

The term crowd in the greatest part of literature is referred to a group of people without strict quantification. Crowd density aims to estimate the number of people in square meters as mentioned in [9]. There are different examples of crowds such as political demonstrations, festivals, sports Olympics or religious events like Hajj in Makkah. These kinds of events require professional controlling and management since they include a huge number of people gathered in a specific place. Crowd management can be defined as the process of detecting, monitoring, tracking, and using a robust decision support system to anticipate and prevent possible crowd related risks [3]. Most research addressing crowd-related concerns has predominantly concentrated on one of these areas: crowd modeling, crowd monitoring, and crowd management. Crowd modeling involves the application of various simulation tools, as extensively detailed in this survey [10]. In contrast, crowd monitoring primarily relies on computer vision methods, as outlined in [3, 11]. Crowd modeling and crowd monitoring research share a common overarching objective, which is to enhance crowd management.

C. Face Detection and Recognition in Crowd

Face recognition technology has numerous applications in crowded spaces. Face detection is used for counting the number of people in crowded places [12]. They designed an application to easily estimate the head count in a photograph using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). The application was tested for preventing crowd in a predefined area during the COVID-19 pandemic. The author in [13] has asserted the importance of face recognition technology in alleviating crowd density overestimation. Authors in [14] highlighted the issue of people entering or leaving the scene or becoming obscured in dynamic environments, which can cause fluctuations in head counts. To address these challenges in video crowd counting, a solution called Locality-constrained Spatial Transformer Network (LSTN) was used, which is a face recognition application for finding missing persons in crowd [5]. A significant application of face recognition is demonstrated in [13] for security purposes where the technique of Local Binary Patterns Histogram (LBPH) is applied with images that were captured by drones. The suggested approach can be followed to enhance surveillance systems by identifying individuals of interest, and thus helps prevent crimes, identify suspects, and enhance public safety. Facial Expression Recognition (FER) can be utilized in analyzing crowd mood to classify people into different groups [16]. Face recognition can be also utilized in access control systems [17], allowing for secure and convenient entry into buildings or gathering events. On the other hand,

face tracking and face recognition are two complementary monitoring systems. Face tracking focuses on real-time tracking of individuals within a given area, while face recognition focuses on identifying and matching faces on a database [7]. Face tracking can be implemented to monitor crowd movements, identify suspicious behavior, or track individuals of interest [18] without the need for tracking tools such as wearable techniques, GPS or mobile, and this is known as Tracking By Detection (TBD) [19]. Face recognition, on the other hand, can be used to identify specific individuals, and provide valuable information about their whereabouts and activities. When utilized together, these technologies can provide comprehensive monitoring and surveillance capabilities. Face recognition and tracking technology employment raises several challenges and ethical concerns as discussed elaborately in [20]. One major anxiety is the potential for bias and discrimination, as the technology may not accurately identify individuals from certain racial or ethnic backgrounds. Privacy maintenance is also a significant matter, as the technology collects and stores personal data. Additionally, there are concerns regarding the technology misuse by governments or law enforcement agencies, leading to mass surveillance and violation of civil liberties. It is crucial to address these fears and establish ethical guidelines to ensure responsible and fair technology use [21]. In contrast, face recognition and tracking technology offer several benefits, including enhanced security, improved efficiency, and personalized experiences. It can help law enforcement agencies identify, and track criminals [22]. It can also streamline processes in various industries, such as banking and airports, by providing quick and secure access to services. Advanced face recognition with surveillance systems has upgraded the civil aviation smart security screening in China [23].

D. Challenges of Face Detection in Crowded Places

Detecting faces in a crowd has several challenges [24, 25], which are discussed below:

- Occlusion which refers to the situation where a part of a person's face is obscured or hidden from view, often by an object, e.g. sunglasses, a hat, a scarf, or a mask or another person. Occlusion can pose a significant difficulty to face detection algorithms because the shown part of the face may not contain enough visual information for the algorithm to accurately detect and recognize it.
- Lighting can affect the contrast and brightness of a person's face, making it either easier or more challenging for a face detection system to identify and locate faces accurately. Bad illumination can be caused by low harsh lights or varying lighting conditions, especially in video senses.
- Pose refers to the orientation or position of a person's face in a scene. Face detection systems need to consider variations in pose because faces can appear in different orientations and angles. The pose of a face can be categorized into several aspects. Frontal pose is often considered the easiest for face detection because the facial features are well-aligned and easily recognizable. Another pose is the profile pose where a person's face is turned to the side, making one or both sides of the face not visible to

the camera. The most challenging pose in face detection is the extreme pose which involves faces that are highly tilted, rotated, or otherwise not aligned with the camera. Advanced deep learning models, such as pose-invariant face recognition networks, have been developed to handle a wide range of pose variations during face recognition tasks [26].

- Facial expressions are highly variable and can change rapidly. A person's face can go through numerous expressions in a short period, making it challenging to detect and recognize a face consistently.
- In face size variability, faces can appear in images or scenes at various scales, ranging from close-up portraits to tiny faces in a crowd or distant surveillance footage. Detecting faces at different scales can be tough, especially when a face is very small or low in resolution.

E. Process Mining

Process mining [27] is a discipline within the field of Business Process Management (BPM) that focuses on analyzing and improving business processes using data-driven techniques. It entails the extraction and analysis of data from event logs, which record the activities and actions taken within an organization's IT systems [28]. The three primary goals of process mining are to discover processes automatically, measure the process compliance with business rules and optimize the process flow and performance. Process mining incorporates analyzing and visualizing processes based on event data. This tool can be used to track and understand the movement and interactions of individuals in crowded areas.

F. The Feasibility of using Process Mining as Trajectory Modeling

In this research we aim to demonstrate the potential of employing process mining to visualize traces of groups of persons. This includes tracking individuals' movements over time and across different locations. Some analogies emerge between the modeling of process flows and crowd flows, revealing similarities and differences. A set of fundamental elements is essential to gain insights into the process within the process mining context. These elements comprise case identification (case ID), activity name, and timestamps (time). Conversely, in the context of crowd flow analysis, the notion of case ID takes on a distinct connotation, distinguishing and categorizing the trajectories of individual entities within a crowd, while the activity and its related time have often the same meaning from the process perspective. A comparison between process flow and crowd flow is shown in Table I. Data Elements in process flow encompass case identification (Case ID), activity naming (Activity Name), and time-related data (Time). In contrast, crowd flow primarily involves the tracking of individual entities within a given location, specifying their identity, position (location), and time. Temporal dynamics in process flow typically consists of a sequence of events, each timestamped for analysis, whereas crowd flow involves concurrent, real-time movements of individuals within a space, which often form dynamic patterns. Modeling techniques differ. Process flow employs process models, such as Petri nets or BPMN, whereas crowd flow utilizes spatial models like

density maps and simulations to represent the movements of individuals or entities. Metrics and KPIs used for assessment diverge as well—process flow relies on measures of efficiency, cycle time, and compliance, while crowd flow assesses crowd density, flow rates, and safety metrics. Visualization techniques also contrast: process flow is often represented with flowcharts or process models, whereas crowd flow uses density heatmaps and flow diagrams. Both areas find applications in various domains, but application areas differ: process flow is commonly found in manufacturing, IT, and healthcare, whereas crowd flow analysis is pertinent to events, transportation hubs, and urban planning. Challenges are varying: process flow addresses bottlenecks, compliance, and automation, whereas crowd flow considers safety, congestion, and crowd management. Considerations regarding regulatory compliance differ as well, with process flow adhering to industry standards and crowd flow adhering to safety regulations and crowd control measures. Lastly, future directions point towards automation and AI-driven optimization in process flow, while crowd flow explores applications in smart cities and continues to analyze crowd behavior.

TABLE I. ANALOGIES AND DISTINCTIONS BETWEEN PROCESS FLOW AND CROWD FLOW

Aspect	Process flow	Crowd flow
Data elements	CaseID, activity name, time	Individual/entity, location, time
Temporal Dynamics	Sequential, time-stamped events	Concurrent, real-time movement
Modeling techniques	Process models (Petri nets, BPMN)	Spatial models (e.g. density maps, simulations)
Metrics and KPIs	Process efficiency, cycle time, compliance	Crowd density, flow rate, safety
Visualization	Process flowcharts, Gantt charts	Density heatmaps, flow diagrams
Application areas	Manufacturing, IT, healthcare	Events, transportation hubs, urban planning
Challenges	Bottlenecks, compliance, automation	Safety, congestion, crowd management and emergent behavior
Regulatory considerations	Compliance with industry standards	Safety regulations, crowd control measures
Future directions	Automation, AI-driven optimization	Smart cities, crowd behavior analysis

II. CROWD MANAGEMENT AT THE HOLY MOSQUE IN MAKKAH CITY: A CASE STUDY

The holy mosque in Makkah is the largest mosque in the world. It has been expanded multiple times and can accommodate around 3 million visitors [29]. Every year pilgrims visit the holy mosque to perform Ramadan or Hajj rituals, and form a significant mass gathering religious events. Integrating video surveillance with face recognition and tracking technology can provide a powerful monitoring and surveillance solution for this kind of crowd. Moreover, analyzing live video feeds allows identifying and tracking individuals in real-time, providing valuable information to security personnel. This integration can enhance the effectiveness of video surveillance systems by automating the identification and tracking procedures, reducing the reliance on manual monitoring. Our hypothesis in this research states that

engaging in frequent visits in a limited timeframe can greatly contribute to the congestion and stampede risks within the Holy Mosque. Consequently, the implementation of a visitor re-identification trajectory can serve as an enhanced tool for crowd monitoring and management.

III. THE PROPOSED SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed system architecture is presented in Figure 1, which includes several steps: image collecting and pre-processing, face detection, face recognition, building event log and then visualizing trajectory model, which is the expected outcome of our proposed approach. The system is run on two stages: the first stage includes all steps except the recognition which occurs at the upcoming stages. The Deepface Python package acts as a framework for our experiment since it includes a set of deep learning algorithms that can be utilized for detection and recognition [30].

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed system architecture.

A. Image Collecting and Preprocessing

Videos were downloaded from the Holy Mosque streamline public channel. We downloaded 4 videos that represent important religious events, which are the prayers of night (Isha), prayerA1, and late night (Tahajud), prayerB1, of the night of the 27th of the fasting month, and the prayers of night (Isha), prayerA2, and late night (Tahajud), prayerB2, of the night of 29th. This selection is based on our prior knowledge of the rituals. There is a possibility of re-identifying the same visitors as some people prefer to stay at the Holy Mosque to perform two subsequent prayers (Isha and Tahajud, which are prayerA and prayerB respectively), since the time interval between them is expected to be 3 hours only. The downloaded videos entail several thumbnails that do not contain any faces. Therefore, manual filtering is applied on the extracted frames to exclude the ones with no faces.

TABLE II. DATASET USED IN THIS RESEARCH

Video	Length	Frame	Frames containing faces
Video 1	01:18	324	52
Video 2	01:54	157	61
Video 3	01:42	601	73
Video 4	01:26	518	45

The images are tagged manually based on the resolution quality into 3 categories: high, low, and mixed resolution images.

B. Detection

There are several face detectors in the literature [31, 32], however, the Retina model [33] is adopted in this paper due to its powerful results of face detection in crowds. It can detect tiny faces due to its algorithm that depends on allocating face landmarks. The Retina model is a pretrained model which uses the WIDER FACE dataset that is a well-known face detection benchmark [34]. It consists of 32,203 carefully selected images derived from the publicly accessible WIDER pedestrian dataset [35]. The WIDER FACE dataset has 393,703 labeled faces with significant variability in terms of scale, pose, and occlusion. The Retina model is a single-stage dense face localization that integrated the existing regression and box classification methods to localize faces in images and then identify 5 face landmarks on top of the existing techniques. It aimed to generate dense 3D face vertices which improved model accuracy in detecting faces in variable scales. The model does not produce a single vector length as an output. Instead, it generates bounding boxes around the detected faces along with the associated facial landmarks. These bounding boxes and landmarks are used to localize and describe the identified faces within the image as pixel coordinates. The model can detect and align faces in different image settings such as blurred, occluded, and partial images. It can also allocate overwritten faces captured from live streaming videos. The 4 downloaded videos are ordered chronologically, hence Video1 represents the first event (prayerA1) and is engaged to run the first stage of the proposed system.

C. Recognition

Face recognition comes after face detection. It focuses on generating a face representation or embedding to be compared later with image pair or a database of images for verification or identification. The VGG-Face recognizer is employed in our experiment due to its robustness [36]. It is a model pretrained in the LFW (Labelled Faces in the Wild) dataset that has 2.6 M images with over 2.6K people [6]. The VGGFace model produces a vector representation of 2622 length. This model achieves high recognition rate with optimum computational performance [30].

D. Building Event Log

The event log is the key component of process mining. It must have three main elements: Visitor ID, which is a random generated number assigned for a visitor when her/his face is detected. Timestamp is the time when a face is observed in the target place. Event name which is a domain-related element in our experiment. Four video of prayers were used. Each video name represents an event, namely prayerA1, prayerB1, prayerA2, and prayerB2. Other attributes can enrich the event log file, and give more insight into the trajectory model. In our case, the image source is stored to help analyze the trajectory model. Also, face bounding box points can be stored as well to facilitate refereeing to the face location in the source image stored in the database for further analysis. The event log is usually saved as a CSV file and then converted to XES

(eXtensible Event Stream) that is the standard format for process mining supported by most process mining tools. A sample of the created event log is presented in Table III. It shows 11 detected faces, where 7 faces are detected from the same image source "img1", 2 faces are detected from "img4", and 1 face is detected from each of "img2" and "img3". The temporal information associated with the observed faces is retrieved using a standard Optical Character Reader (OCR) embedded within the video.

TABLE III. EVENT LOG SAMPLE

Index	Face_id	Date&Time	Event	Source_img	Img_resolution	Face coordinates
0	2456	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[100,50,200,150]
1	7638	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[20,30,100,80]
2	5162	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[10,10,90,120]
3	0918	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[200,50,300,250]
4	1632	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[75,65,155,185]
5	8374	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[30,40,110,130]
6	6348	20/4/2023 00:33	prayerB1	Img1	high	[90,20,120,170]
7	9877	20/4/2023 01:40	prayerB1	Img2	mixed	[15,25,95,85]
8	0914	21/4/2023 09:40	prayerA2	Img3	mixed	[40,50,120,140]
9	5412	21/4/2023 09:45	prayerA2	Img4	low	[10,30,170,80]
10	7810	21/4/2023 09:45	prayerA2	Img4	low	[25,25,105,125]

E. Computational Complexity Analysis of the Proposed System

- **Face Detection step:** The computational complexity of face detection depends on the algorithm used. Suppose the detection algorithm processes each image with a time complexity of $O(N)$. If there are M images in total, the complexity for face detection is $O(M \cdot N)$.
- **Database Operations step:** Adding a face to the database and finding a matching face depend on the data structure utilized for the database. If we assume a basic list structure, adding a face has a time complexity of $O(1)$ on average, while finding a matching face can be $O(K)$, where K is the number of faces in the database. Since these operations are performed for each new face in each new image, the overall complexity is $O(M \cdot K)$, where M is the number of new images and K is the total number of faces in the database.
- **Event Log step:** Appending to the event log has a time complexity of $O(1)$ per entry, and this operation is performed for each detected face in each new image, resulting in a complexity of $O(M)$.
- **Visualization step:** The complexity of visualizing the trajectory depends on the visualization method, but for simplicity, let us assume it is $O(N)$, where N is the number of entries in the event log. Overall, the total computational

complexity of the algorithm is the sum of the complexities for each step:

$$\text{Total Complexity} = O(M \cdot N) + O(M \cdot K) + O(M) + O(N) \quad (1)$$

The dominant terms are typically the ones with the highest growth rate. In many cases, the face detection step ($O(M \cdot N)$) and the database operations ($O(M \cdot K)$) dominate the complexity.

IV. RESULTS

The created event log can be imported to any process mining tool for visualizing a trajectory model. In this research, the Python library for process mining PM4Py [4] was used for generating the graph-based trajectory model. The process model discovery algorithm represents an event name in the event log into a node. The edges connecting the nodes have labels that show the number of visitors who are observed in the corresponding events. In Figure 2, there are 1131 visitors who were observed in the first event prayerA1 and were not observed to the other selected events. However, 534 out of 1355 visitors who attended prayerA2, were re-identified later, in the video of the following event prayerB2.

Using the proposed method, a list of shots in which the person of interest appears in each matching video is retrieved. Interestingly, recognition rate was high for faces detected from high resolution images, and thus the model showed the same person appearing in different prayers (Figure 3). On the other hand, recognizing persons captured in low resolution increased the false positive recognition rate as shown in Figure 4. The face id 91017 was given to a person in img 29 0661, who was observed in prayerA2 and then the same id was given to two more persons who were actually different. This false positive is probably due to the very low-resolution of the image. We believe that readjusting camera positions in crowd places can result in better image resolution and consequently, low false positive recognition.

Fig. 2. Trajectory representation of recognized faces.

Fig. 3. Trajectory model of true positive face re-identification.

Fig. 4. Trajectory model of true positive face re-identification.

V. DISCUSSION

Utilizing process mining techniques is proved to be advantageous in constructing trajectory models. Nevertheless, the model effectiveness is significantly reliant on the availability of data elements within the event log. Therefore, the process of generating the event log and integrating diverse data sources is of utmost importance. It is essential to be cautious when using face recognition models on unlabeled identities, as the absence of multiple shots per identity makes it more challenging to quantify performance accurately. It is also crucial to consider the potential ethical implications of employing face recognition technologies in scenarios involving unlabeled identities to ensure fairness and privacy. We

recommend applying image pre-processing for enhancing face resolution before the recognition phase [37]. Given the potential privacy and ethical concerns associated with face recognition and tracking technology, it is essential to establish regulations and guidelines for its ethical use. This includes ensuring transparency in how the technology is implemented, obtaining informed consent, and protecting personal data. Governments and regulatory bodies should work together with technology developers, privacy advocates, and other stakeholders to develop and enforce these regulations. By doing so, we can ensure that the technology is used responsibly and in a manner that respects individuals' privacy rights. It should be noted that, several countries and jurisdictions have started implementing legal frameworks and guidelines for face recognition technology usage in public spaces. These frameworks aim to balance the need for public safety with the protection of individuals' privacy rights. They outline the conditions under which the technology can be utilized, the limitations on data collection and storage, and the rights of individuals regarding their personal data. It is crucial for governments to continuously review and update these frameworks to keep pace with the technological advancements, and address emerging challenges. One of the major concerns with face recognition systems is the potential for bias and inaccuracy, particularly when it comes to identifying individuals from certain racial or ethnic backgrounds. This raises concerns about discrimination and the potential for false identifications. To address these concerns, it is important to ensure diversity in the datasets engaged to train the algorithms and to continuously evaluate and eliminate the bias. Hence, we aim to use the extracted faces to retrain the model and improve feature extraction. Face recognition and tracking technology can significantly enhance public safety. By identifying and tracking individuals of interest, law enforcement agencies can prevent crimes, locate suspects, and respond more effectively to incidents. The technology can be integrated with existing surveillance systems to provide real-time alerts and notifications when a person of interest is detected.

Another essential finding of this research is that, to build a robust human recognition system in unconstrained environment, the system should include more elements than plain face recognition, e.g. body features and movement should be integrated as well. Despite the advancements in face recognition and tracking technology, there are still limitations that need to be overcome. One limitation is the technology accuracy, particularly in challenging lighting conditions, or when faces are partially obscured, which can result in misidentifications. To overcome such limitations, researchers and developers are working on ameliorating the algorithms employed in the technology, as well as enhancing the hardware and software components.

VI. CONCLUSION

The future of face recognition technology holds great promise. Advancements in artificial intelligence, machine learning, and computer vision are expected to further improve the accuracy, speed, and capabilities of face recognition and tracking systems. This includes advancements in facial expression recognition, emotion detection, and the ability to

identify individuals in challenging conditions. Additionally, process mining technique has shown its capabilities in modelling the trajectory of faces in crowds. Further research and development in technology to enable automatic texture face trajectory will help analyze crowd behavior. These advancements will continue to expand the applications of face recognition technology in various industries, and contribute to safer and better crowd monitoring systems. There are also serious concerns regarding privacy and ethical use. It is crucial to establish clear regulations and guidelines to ensure responsible and fair implementation of these technologies.

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Evaluation of Energy Renovation Measures for Hospital Buildings using the PSI Method

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the potential for energy savings and reduction in CO₂ emissions in hospital buildings in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H), through the implementation of energy renovation measures. The building sector in B&H is characterized by significant energy consumption, and hospitals account for a substantial portion of the total energy consumption in public buildings. This study analyzes certain energy renovation measures for selected hospital buildings, including the installation of thermal insulation on exterior walls and flat roofs, and the installation of a photovoltaic plant on the flat roof. The Preference Selection Index (PSI) multicriteria decision-making method was employed to evaluate and rank renovation scenarios based on energy, environmental, and financial criteria. The results indicate that the most preferred measure is the installation of a photovoltaic plant on a flat roof, resulting in significant primary energy and CO₂ savings, with an acceptable discounted payback period. The findings emphasize the effectiveness of energy renovation measures in enhancing energy efficiency and reducing the environmental impact of hospital buildings in B&H.

Keywords-hospital building; multicriteria analysis; PSI; energy consumption; energy efficiency, renewable energy; photovoltaic plant

I. INTRODUCTION

The building sector in Bosnia and Herzegovina (B&H), is the leading energy consumer, exceeding both the transport and industry sectors [1]. This sector is characterized by buildings with significant losses in transmission and ventilation, and thermal systems with low overall efficiency, suggesting substantial potential for energy savings through energy renovation measures [2-3]. In recent years, numerous renovation projects have been implemented in the B&H public sector, highlighting the need to improve energy efficiency in public buildings. The healthcare buildings in B&H [4] include a significant number of hospital buildings, representing 13% of the total heated area of all public buildings [3]. Within healthcare buildings, buildings constructed between 1974 and

1987 account for 44% of the total heated area and 50.6% of the total energy consumption, offering substantial potential for energy savings. Hospital buildings, due to their specific purpose, occupational regime, and design parameters with high internal temperature, are of particular importance and require careful analysis, especially to ensure appropriate internal microclimatic conditions [4]. As the energy consumption of hospital buildings is high, there is a significant potential for energy savings through the implementation of active and passive energy restoration measures [5-8]. These measures can lead to improved energy efficiency, reduced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and an overall improvement in building structures [9]. In [6], a novel concept called "70-70-70" was proposed to significantly reduce GHG emissions in hospitals and contribute to the global goal of achieving a clean and

climate neutral environment by 2050. This concept aims to achieve three key targets: a 70% reduction in the building's GHG emissions, utilization of renewable energy for 70% of the total energy consumption, and a 70% increase in the building's energy efficiency. This concept was tested in two existing buildings, showing that the proposed solutions led to a reduction of more than 70% in annual primary energy consumption. In [7], a survey was conducted in 12 hospitals and 70 healthcare centers in Spain, built between 1980 and 2005. This study focused on electric energy, Heating Ventilation and Air-Conditioning (HVAC), Domestic Water Heating (DWH), lighting systems, renewable energy, maintenance strategy, thermal insulation, and optimal building size. The study concluded that it is possible to save a significant amount of energy in healthcare buildings. In [8], focus was given on identifying and classifying passive strategies for energy optimization in the design of sustainable hospitals and health centers. This study was carried out in hospitals located in Shiraz, Iran, and used questionnaires, interviews, and literature as information-collecting tools. The data were analyzed using two Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods: the Best-Worst Method (BWM) and Evaluation based on the Distance from the Average Solution (EDAS). The identified passive strategies were classified into three groups, thermal, acoustic, and lighting strategies, and each category was then prioritized. The most important selection criteria were "Reducing Energy Consumption", "Compatibility with Climate", and "Durability". The most suitable passive strategies in the thermal, acoustic, and lighting groups were "Optimizing Fenestration Design", "Using Naturally Ventilated Envelope", and "Using Sun Shading Devices", respectively. The study concluded that applying its results in the design of hospitals and health centers could reduce energy consumption.

The current study aims to analyze the best energy renovation scenario for a hospital building, using the Preference Selection Index (PSI) MCDM. MCDM is widely used in engineering [10-11] to support the decision-making process. The versatility of MCDM in the field of energy production and utilization is confirmed by its successful application of a modified VIKOR method [12], providing a comprehensive analysis of the optimal energy mix for national or local communities. The selected hospital building was constructed in 1980, with energy-inefficient envelope characteristics and thermotechnical systems. Seven scenarios were considered and evaluated, consisting of individual and combined measures, including energy renovation of the envelope and installation of a photovoltaic plant on a flat roof. For each scenario, the primary energy, carbon footprint, investment cost, and Discounted Payback Period (DPP) were calculated, which were also considered as MCDM criteria to evaluate and rank the renovation scenarios.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Building Data

The selected hospital building is located in Sarajevo, B&H, and is part of a large hospital complex of 35,800 m² of heated area, while the building itself has 4,883 m² of heated area (13.6% of the total hospital building complex). The hospital

complex is equipped with a central boiler room with highly efficient industrial steam boilers, with energy for heating and DWH supplied to the buildings via heating substations. Natural gas is used as a fuel and the system efficiency of the components, including the boiler room and the heating substation, is 95.04%. Two water tanks are installed at the heating substation for the DWH system. A radiator heating system is used for building heating without a mechanical ventilation system. The efficiency of the heating system inside the building (regulation and distribution system) is 98%, therefore the overall system efficiency including the boiler room, distribution, and internal installations and components is 93.1%. A central cooling system is installed, but it only serves a small portion of the building.

Fig. 1. Visual representation of the selected hospital building.

The building was constructed in 1980, and consists of a basement, ground floor, and four floors, with a flat roof, as shown in Figure 1. The building occupational regime is established on a permanent basis, with 365 operating days a year and 24 operating hours a day. In 2017-2018, old windows with aluminum profiles were replaced with new wooden frame windows. The new windows have a triple-pane insulating glass filled with argon and a heat transfer coefficient of 1.0 W/m²K, aligned with the national regulations that target a U_{win} of 1.4 W/m²K for new windows installed in existing properties [4]. The energy renovation resulted in a reduction in heat loss and improved thermal comfort. However, no other energy renovation measures were implemented, leading to ongoing energy losses due to the low energy efficiency of the building envelope. Table I provides details about the building structure, including the total area of the base, the heated surface area, and the compactness ratio of the building. Table I also provides the heat transfer coefficients of the key construction elements. The external wall was constructed of clay blocks, without any thermal insulation. The flat roof was constructed from a reinforced concrete slab with 4 cm of thermal insulation. Based on [4], it was determined that the heat transfer coefficient of the external wall was significantly higher than the requirements set by national regulations, implying that this building's elements contribute to excessive energy losses.

TABLE I. DATA ON BUILDING GEOMETRY AND HEAT TRANSFER COEFFICIENT OF CONSTRUCTION ELEMENTS

Building parameters	Value
Number of floors	B+G+4
Net area of the heated space	4,698 m ²
The volume of the heated space	16,787 m ³
Building compactness ratio	0.28
External wall surface area	2,260 m ²
Heat transfer coefficient of external wall	1.698 W/m ² K
Windows surface area	1,216 m ²
Heat transfer coefficient of windows	1.0 W/m ² K
Roof surface area	923 m ²
Heat transfer coefficient of roof	0.602 W/m ² K

B. Modeling of Building Energy Performance

The energy performance of the building was modeled with the DesignBuilder software and its integrated EnergyPlus simulation tool [13]. Figure 2 shows a 3D model of the hospital building designed in DesignBuilder.

Fig. 2. 3D model of hospital building.

EnergyPlus uses hourly data for environmental conditions and calculations. Climatic data, monitored by the National Meteorological Service, include air temperature, atmospheric conditions, solar radiation, wind speed and direction, and are specific to the analyzed location (Sarajevo). The city is in a northern climate zone, with 43.85 latitude and 18.14 longitude, characterized by hot summers and cold and snowy winters. The Heating Degree Days (HDD) value for Sarajevo is 3,077. The warmest month is typically July, with an average temperature of 20.8°C, while the coldest month, January, averages 0.7°C. Solar radiation is highest in July and lowest in December [14]. Climatic data are essential to understanding the energy performance of buildings, as they directly impact heating and cooling needs and the potential for solar energy utilization.

The zoning of the building's interior space is performed according to the hospital layout with internal design temperatures of each zone specified by the BAS EN 12831 standard. The simulation results include the energy needs for heating, DWH, and electrical energy. The energy consumption of the cooling system is included in the electrical energy consumption, under the assumption that cooling is facilitated by devices with a coefficient of performance of 3. The total primary energy E_{Prim} is calculated using the following equation:

$$E_{Prim} = \frac{Q_{H,nd} + Q_{DWH}}{\eta_{sist}} f_{p,gas} + E_{El} f_{p,el} \quad (1)$$

where E_{Prim} is the building's annual primary energy (kWh/a), $Q_{H,nd}$ is the annual energy need for heating (kWh/a), Q_{DWH} is the annual energy need for DWH (kWh/a), η_{sist} is the overall system efficiency (%), E_{El} is the annual electrical energy consumption from the electrical grid (kWh/a), and f_p is the fuel primary energy factor (1.1 for natural gas and 1.614 for electricity) [4]. The annual CO₂ emissions are calculated by:

$$m_{CO_2} = \frac{Q_{H,nd} + Q_{DWH}}{\eta_{sist}} c_{p,gas} + E_{El} c_{p,el} \quad (2)$$

where m_{CO_2} is the annual CO₂ emission (kg/a) and c_p is the fuel CO₂ coefficient per unit of energy (0.2 kg/kWh for natural gas and 0.745 kg/kWh for electricity) [4]. Electrical energy is calculated as the total electric energy reduced by the electricity generated from the photovoltaic plant, which impacts the reduction of CO₂ emissions as well.

C. Energy Renovation Measures

To reduce the energy consumption and carbon emissions of the building, certain energy renovation measures were analyzed, including the installation of thermal insulation on the external walls and flat roof, and the installation of a photovoltaic plant on the flat roof. Previous energy-saving initiatives included window replacement, lighting system upgrades, and the installation of a modern central heating plant with new gas boilers. The current focus was on enhancing envelope characteristics and thermal comfort and incorporating renewable energy systems. These immediate energy-saving measures could be followed by future analysis of other energy-saving strategies, all to create a clean, climate-neutral environment.

The first measure (M1) considers the installation of 20 cm of rock wool as thermal insulation on the external wall. Rock wool is known for its excellent thermal properties, characterized by a low thermal conductivity of 0.033 W/mK, and offers additional benefits such as improved acoustics, indoor comfort, and fire safety. Implementing this measure will accordingly reduce the external wall heat transfer coefficient, improving the thermal comfort of the building by minimizing heat losses. Insulation will protect the building construction against weathering, thus increasing its lifespan. The cost of investment for this measure is € 101,023. The second measure (M2) considers installing thermal insulation on the flat roof using 25 cm perlite board with a thermal conductivity of 0.052 W/mK. As a result, the heat transfer coefficient of the roof will decrease, reducing heat loss through the roof surface area. The estimated investment cost for this measure is € 63,575. Installation of a photovoltaic plant on a flat roof is the third measure (M3). The surface area available for the installation of photovoltaic panels is an essential factor in determining the plant power output, which in this case is estimated to be 80 kW. The panels should be strategically oriented to the south and mounted at an optimal angle to maximize energy production. Photovoltaic panels convert solar energy into electrical energy, thereby providing a renewable source of electricity and reducing energy costs and carbon footprint. The estimated cost of investment for this measure is € 57,905.

The cost of investment for all three measures includes all associated expenses such as labor, materials, and actions involved in the renovation process, including demolition, assembly, installation, and disposal of materials and equipment. This method was selected due to its detailed approach, which considers a wide range of factors and costs associated with an investment [15] and ensures that the calculated cost is realistic and reflects all aspects of the investment process. In the context of a multicriteria analysis, individual measures are evaluated separately and combined into groups, resulting in seven renovation scenarios. For each scenario, the resulting primary energy, carbon footprint, and investment cost were calculated.

D. Financial Indicators

The Discounted Payback Period (DPP) was used to evaluate the profitability of the renovation scenarios. This measures the time it takes for the initial investment to be returned in terms of discounted cash flows, thus considering the time value of money. DPP is a valuable tool in capital budgeting, helping businesses make informed investment decisions. The average cost of the final energy for natural gas and electricity was determined from hospital bills and was 0.072 €/kWh and 0.097 €/kWh, respectively. Using these data, the annual energy cost and the annual energy cost savings were calculated for each renovation scenario. In this study, the DPP was calculated using the method of [16], with a capital cost of 5.5%. A shorter DPP indicates a quicker return on the initial investment.

E. Preference Selection Index Method

The Preference Selection Index (PSI) is a MCDM technique used to solve various decision-making problems without the need to assign relative importance or weights to criteria [17]. The PSI method has been used to solve decision-making problems in various fields, such as material selection [18], manufacturing [19], solar system application possibilities [20], etc. Compared to other MCDM methods, PSI is simpler and less computationally demanding. The procedure of evaluating and ranking the alternatives with the PSI method is described below.

- Step 1 - Definition of decision matrix: For a decision-making problem with m alternatives and n criteria, the decision matrix can be defined in the following mathematical form:

$$X = [x_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & \cdots & x_{1j} & \cdots & x_{1n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{i1} & \cdots & x_{ij} & \cdots & x_{in} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & \cdots & x_{mj} & \cdots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where x_{ij} is the performance of alternative i concerning criterion j .

- Step 2 - Decision matrix normalization: The decision matrix is normalized using the max normalization method

depending on the type of criteria. The normalized performances of alternatives are calculated using the following equation:

$$R = [r_{ij}]_{m \times n} = \begin{cases} \frac{x_{ij}}{\max_i x_{ij}} & j \in \mathcal{B} \\ \frac{\min_i x_{ij}}{x_{ij}} & j \in \mathcal{C} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{B} is beneficial and \mathcal{C} non-beneficial criteria.

- Step 3 - Calculation of preference variation: The preference variation for each criterion is calculated using the following equation:

$$PV = [pv_j]_{1 \times n} = \sum_{i=1}^m (r_{ij} - \bar{r}_j)^2 \quad (5)$$

where \bar{r}_j is the mean of the normalized criterion j and:

$$\bar{r}_j = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m r_{ij}.$$

- Step 4 - Determination of overall preference: In this step, the overall performance is calculated for each criterion. Before calculating the overall preference, it is necessary to first calculate preference deviation $\Phi = [\phi_j]_{1 \times n}$ in the preference value PV. The deviation in the preference value of each criterion is calculated by:

$$\Phi = [\phi_j]_{1 \times n} = 1 - pv_j \quad (6)$$

The overall preference of each criterion is calculated by:

$$\Psi = [\psi_j]_{1 \times n} = \frac{\phi_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \phi_j} \quad (7)$$

The sum of overall preferences for all criteria is equal to 1:

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \psi_j = 1$$

- Step 5 - Calculation of PSI: The PSI for each alternative is calculated by:

$$PSI = [psi_i]_{m \times 1} = \sum_{j=1}^n r_{ij} \psi_j \quad (8)$$

- Step 6 - Ranking alternatives: Alternatives are ranked according to their PSI in descending order so that the alternative with the highest PSI is ranked the first and the alternative with the lowest PSI is the last.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For each renovation scenario, the resulting primary energy, carbon footprint, cost of investment, energy cost savings, and DPP were calculated.

A. Building Energy Performances of Renovation Scenarios

Table II presents the building parameters, including the heat transfer coefficients of the walls and roofs, before and after the renovation, and the installed power of the photovoltaic system. Data show that the implementation of measures M1 and M2 results in a decrease in the heat transfer coefficient of the building envelope, following the national regulations [4]. The installed power of the photovoltaic plant is 80 kW.

TABLE II. BUILDING PARAMETERS BEFORE AND AFTER RENOVATIONS

Measure	Parameter	Baseline	After renovation	Target value [4]
M1 - Thermal insulation on exterior wall	U_{wall} W/m ² K	1.698	0.272	0.35
M2 - Thermal insulation on flat roof	U_{roof} W/m ² K	0.602	0.218	0.25
M3 - Photovoltaic plant	P_{pv} kW	0	80	-

Table III shows the calculated values of the primary energy, CO₂ emissions, cost of investment, and DPP for each renovation scenario. It also shows the energy cost savings associated with each renovation scenario.

TABLE III. RESULTING ENERGY, ENVIRONMENTAL AND FINANCIAL INDICATORS

Scenario	E_{prim} (MWh/a)	CO ₂ (t/a)	Investment (€)	Cost savings (€/a)	DPP year
Baseline	1,780	477.8	-	-	-
S1: M1	1,565	438.9	101,023	14,206	9.3
S2: M2	1,718	466.5	63,575	4,067	36.8
S3: M1,2	1,527	432.5	164,598	18,273	12.9
S4: M3	1,642	413.2	57,905	8,287	9.1
S5: M1,3	1,427	374.3	158,928	22,492	9.2
S6: M2,3	1,580	402.0	121,480	12,354	14.7
S7: M1,2,3	1,389	367.9	222,503	25,007	12.7

Implementing the M1 measure results in an annual savings of 215 MWh of primary energy with a DPP of 9.3 years. Implementing the M2 measure results in the least primary energy savings, approximately 62 MWh per year. This measure also has a significantly longer DPP, which is expected since the existing roof structure already includes 4 cm of thermal insulation. Therefore, the implementation of this measure leads to modest savings in energy and CO₂ emissions with a significant investment cost. Implementing measure M3 results in high primary energy savings and the highest CO₂ emission savings compared to the other two measures, exhibiting the shortest DPP. The S5 renovation scenario, which involves installing thermal insulation on the exterior walls (M1) and photovoltaic panels on the roof of the building (M3), yields very high primary energy savings and the second shorter DPP, 353 MWh annually and 9.2 years, respectively. These findings indicate that the selected renovation scenario results in a reduction in building energy consumption and an improvement in energy and environmental indicators. This emphasizes the effectiveness of these measures in improving the energy efficiency of the building.

B. Multicriteria Analysis of Renovation Scenarios

The PSI method was used to rank all seven scenarios. Primary energy, CO₂ emission, cost of investment, and DPP were considered non-beneficial criteria and were minimized in the performed analysis. PSI was calculated for each scenario, and scenarios were ranked from 1 (best solution) to 7 (worst solution), as shown in Table IV and Figure 3, which display the scenario rankings and their corresponding PSI values. The best energy renovation scenario was S4 (M3), the installation of a photovoltaic plant on a flat roof, with the highest PSI value of 0.9147. The second-best scenario was S5 (M1+M3), installing thermal insulation on external walls (M1) and photovoltaic

panels on the building's roof (M3), ranked as a better solution than solely implementing M1. The S1 (M1) scenario, installing thermal insulation on external walls, ranked third with a PSI value of 0.8356. Installing thermal insulation on a flat roof (S2) ranked seventh with a PSI value of 0.7154. This is expected, as M2 results in the smallest primary energy and CO₂ savings and has a very long DPP.

TABLE IV. RANKING OF RENOVATION SCENARIOS

Scenario	Measure	PSI	Rank
S4	M3	0.9147	1
S5	M1+M3	0.8768	2
S1	M1	0.8356	3
S7	M1+M2+M3	0.8229	4
S6	M2+M3	0.7747	5
S3	M1+M2	0.7589	6
S2	M2	0.7154	7

Fig. 3. PSI of renovation scenarios.

Figure 3 shows a visual representation of the PSI values for all the renovation scenarios analyzed. As previously shown in Table IV, the highest PSI was obtained for S4, representing the measure M3, the installation of a photovoltaic plant on a flat roof. The lowest PSI was obtained for S2, representing measure M2 (installing thermal insulation on the flat roof).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study analyzed the benefits of implementing energy renovation measures in a hospital building in Bosnia and Herzegovina, revealing that there is substantial potential for energy and CO₂ savings. The analysis considered certain energy renovation measures, including the installation of thermal insulation on the exterior wall and the flat roof, and the installation of a photovoltaic plant on the roof. Based on these measures, seven scenarios were generated, consisting of individual measures or their combinations. The resulting primary energy, CO₂ emissions, cost of investment, and DPP were calculated for each renovation scenario. The results demonstrated that energy renovation measures can significantly improve the energy efficiency of hospital buildings, reduce emissions, and contribute to the global objective of achieving a clean and climate-neutral environment, with acceptable DPP. The PSI method was used to evaluate and rank the scenarios and select the best one. The results indicated that the most preferred scenario was S4 - installation of a photovoltaic plant on the flat roof, resulting in a significant reduction in primary energy and carbon footprint and the shortest DPP of 9.1 years. The second-best scenario was S5 - installing thermal insulation

on the exterior walls and photovoltaic panels on the building's roof, resulting in very high primary energy and CO₂ savings with adequate DPP. In conclusion, the evaluation and ranking of renovation scenarios can be successfully performed using the PSI method considering energy, environmental, and financial criteria. The proposed method illustrates the effectiveness of MCDM methods in optimizing the energy renovation process in buildings. These methods are adaptable to a variety of technologies, conditions, and data availability, thus offering a broad spectrum of practical uses and strategic decision-making processes. Future studies could include combined methods of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and MCDM in a similar research problem.

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Geometry Effects on Joint Strength and Failure Modes of Hybrid Aluminum-Composite Countersunk bolted Joints

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the effects of geometry parameters (width/hole diameter, and edge distance/hole diameter ratios) on the damage initiation and growth in the CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer) composite-aluminum countersunk bolted joints. Strain gauge measurements conducted with an Instron testing machine along with a detailed 3D finite element model incorporating geometric, material, and friction-based contact nonlinearities were used to investigate the geometry parameters on the Progressive Damage Analysis (PDA) of the orthotropic material model. The PDA material model integrates the lamina nonlinear shear deformation, Hashin-type failure criteria, and strain-based continuum degradation rules, using the UMAT user subroutine in the MSC Software Corporation Patran-Nastran commercial software. The results showed that the geometry effects on damage initiation and failure modes are quite accurately predicted by the PDA material model, which proved to be computationally efficient, and therefore can predict failure propagation and damage mechanisms. Plate geometry is an important parameter in the design process of an adequate bolted joint while its effects on damage initiation and failure modes were quite accurately predicted by the analysis. The latter proved to be computationally efficient, and could successfully predict failure propagation and damage mechanism in hybrid metal-composite countersunk bolted joints.

Keywords-progressive damage; failure mode; strength

I. INTRODUCTION

The aerospace industry became the most common application field for fiber reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites (PMCs) due to their lightweight properties [1]. These structural components are often assembled in conjunction with metal parts, using mechanically fastened joints, resulting in hybrid metal-composite joints, which generate some challenging problems for mechanical engineers. Poorly designed hybrid joints not only are a source of failure, but could also lead to a reduction of the whole structure

durability and reliability. Researchers commonly study failure analysis of composite bolted joints, using a method that combines Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) [2] with Finite Element Analysis (FEA). In the CDM case, the local damage onset appears at low values of the applied load. Damage accumulation is developed with increasing load according to damage propagation laws, which makes the method accurate, and able to predict various failure modes. The major disadvantage of the CDM models is the huge amount of test data required for model calibration.

Progressive Damage Analysis (PDA) of composite materials, which is based on the stress-strain failure criterion [3], showed that the material orthotropic property reduction due to damage initiation is essential for stress field analysis [4-7]. Intralaminar damage initiation based on the local stress-strain state and the subsequent stiffness degradation that reflects damage were primarily investigated within the framework of CDM. On the contrary, delamination and, to a limited extent, matrix cracking were studied with the help of interface fracture mechanics approaches as cohesive zone models and virtual crack closure techniques. Combining both approaches for the PDA of PMCs is an analysis procedure employed for laminate failure. Matrix microcracking may lead to a split as a localized phenomenon, and then a mesomodel approach [8] can be used. A Discrete Ply Model (DPM) along with cohesive elements placed at the interfaces between solid elements to represent matrix cracks and delamination allow the natural coupling between the intra- and inter-laminar damage to be naturally taken into account. The former can be utilized for a computational study of scaled open-hole tensile tests [9], or for the failure mode called pull-through to test fasteners in laminates [10] where the splitting and load redistribution effects were correctly predicted. Many PDA models [11-15] incorporate shear nonlinearity, the Hashin type failure criterion and constant elastic property degradation laws for orthotropic materials. These make the method quite easy to implement and computationally efficient. Since these property degradation models use constant factors for the elastic property reduction due to damage growth, they cannot predict the bearing final failure. A design methodology for mechanical fastened joints in composite laminates was proposed in [11] to forecast the final failure and failure modes by using point or average stress models. A comprehensive review on the available degradation models for PDA, containing 310 references, was organized in [16] around the relationships of the various models together with the frameworks employed for finite element implementation. A continuum based progressive damage model for fiber-reinforced composites, implemented in ABAQUS, considered two failure modes: catastrophic net-section tension-failure and non-catastrophic accumulation of bearing damage [17]. Models containing continuous degradation rules intending to improve the numeric algorithm convergence, and to obtain a smoother load-displacement curve have started to appear in literature [18, 19]. One major deficiency of these models is that they focus only on a few types of failure modes, and do not consider the various joint failure modes. The composite progressive damage behavior is a complex nonlinear phenomenon, and in conjunction with geometric and contact nonlinearities can lead to convergence loss in the Finite Element Method (FEM) analysis. This mostly occurs in implicit numerical algorithms, which imply that many efforts are made for obtaining a valid solution towards predicting the ultimate global structure failure. Composite materials can withstand an increased temperature up to 300 °C, having favorable properties such as high pressure resistance, low thermal expansion coefficient, high thermal conductivity, high thermal shock resistance, and low depression [20, 21]. The difficulties arising from composite material usage on structural failure problems are that these materials have anisotropic mechanical properties, brittle behavior, and low interlaminar

strength [22]. Another issue is the damage variation with temperature [23-26]. Also, various structures can be exposed to harsh environment conditions that may cause joint strength loss because of environmental aging and temperature variations [27-31].

In this paper, a progressive damage analysis using an adequate material model for a hybrid metal-composite countersunk single bolted joint is described and developed. The numerical model can predict the geometrical parameter (width/hole diameter and edge distance/hole diameter ratios) effects on the structural behavior and failure modes. It takes into account all the nonlinearity phenomena involved in the load transfer through the joint, i.e. geometric nonlinearity (large deformations), friction based full nonlinear contact, and material nonlinearities due to the lamina shear deformations. Hashin-type failure and strain-based continuous degradation model were implemented using a user defined subroutine in the commercial software MSC Nastran SOL 400 solver. A series of standard bearing tests were conducted in the laboratory to validate the three-dimensional finite element model and PDA results. The influence of geometrical parameters on the failure modes of the countersunk hybrid metal-composite joints is a task relevant to the aeronautic field of engineering and maintenance for structural applications. An example is the attachment bolts of the visiting covers on the exterior skin of airplane wings. The experimental and numerical results fit quite accurately capturing the impact of geometrical parameters on stiffness, failure load, and failure modes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Joint Geometry

Single-Lap Joints (SLJs) with countersunk bolts were manufactured using metal and composite materials for the adherents. Joint geometry is presented in Figure 1. The joint design was chosen in accordance with ASTM D 5961 [32] to induce bearing failure. The in-plane dimensions of each plate are illustrated in Table I and Figure 1.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENT SET-UP

Case	No. of specimens	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Edge distance (mm)	e/D (-)	b/D (-)	Bolt torque (Nm)
1	5	150	34	10	2.5	6.8	0.5
2	5	150	42	15	3.75	8.4	0.5
3	5	150	50	20	5	10	0.5

Fig. 1. Countersunk hybrid joint geometry.

Material thicknesses are different, 4 mm for the metal plate and 2 mm for the laminated plate. Countersunk head stainless steel bolts with nominal diameter of 4 mm were used. The applied torque level for the bolt is 0.5 N·m. A similar geometry was utilized in [33]. Special attention is given to the conditions for obtaining bearing failure as: $b/D > 4$, $e/D > 3$, $1.5 \leq D/t \leq 3$, $0 \leq h/t \leq 0.7$ (Figure 1). The shank of the bolt does not bear the hole surface due to the initial clearance in the joint. The joint under investigation has a close tolerance clearance equal to 48 μm according to f7H10 [34]. The hole has therefore a diameter $D = 4.048$ mm.

B. Materials and Specimen Manufacturing

Countersunk head stainless steel bolts in dry conditions were considered. The composite adherent was manufactured from carbon-epoxy pre-preg layers with 32% fiber volume fraction by SC AVI SRL Craiova Dolj. The stacking sequence of the composite laminate adherent is represented by [0/90/0/90/0/90], using 0.33 mm thickness unidirectional lamina with the elastic properties presented in Table II. The aluminum adherent was manufactured from AA 7075T6 aluminum alloy [40] by AMARI Metal Innovations. The standard bolts, nuts, and washers were fabricated from stainless steel A2-70 [40] with the elastic properties presented in Table III. The presented (Table II) lamina elastic properties were obtained experimentally following the ASTM standards [35-37] by performing tests on the unidirectional laminated specimens. The constitutive behavior of the composite material was considered linear for traction and compression and nonlinear for shearing based on the experimental results. The latter were obtained after testing specimens with unidirectional fibers, longitudinal and perpendicular to the fiber direction. Shear deformation was acquired using the Iosipescu test on notched specimens and traction for specimens cut at 45° with respect to the alignment of 0/90° to get fibers at 45°. The lamina orthotropic directions (1, 2, 3) are the same with the global coordinate axes (x, y, z) shown in Figure 1. Regarding the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) of the composite adherent, the micro-analysis method was used to calculate it at lamina level utilizing the coefficients of thermal expansion of fibers and matrix. According to [38, 39] we considered $\alpha_{\text{fiber}} = -0.41 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ and $\alpha_{\text{matrix}} = 40 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$. With these values, it can be obtained [3]:

$$\alpha_{11} = \frac{E_{\text{fiber}} \cdot V_{\text{fiber}} \cdot \alpha_{\text{fiber}} + E_{\text{matrix}} \cdot (1 - V_{\text{fiber}}) \cdot \alpha_{\text{matrix}}}{E_{11}} = 2 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$$

The thermal expansion coefficients on the other two directions are $\alpha_{22} = \alpha_{33} = 44^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$. For the metallic parts of the joint, the material properties were taken from [40].

C. Joint Geometry

SLJs were prepared to study the influence of geometry parameters (width/hole diameter and edge distance/hole diameter ratios) on the failure mechanisms in the laminated adherent. There were no compensation tabs used to align the joint in the grips, considering that this boundary condition is closer to reality in practical applications. Therefore, it was expected to acquire bending effects in the adherents, most of which in the composite ones. After joint mounting, the specimens were gripped in the 30 kN Instron 3367 testing

machine, and were connected to a temperature-controlled chamber [41]. The chamber is Instron SFL 3119-400, temperature-controlled (-70/+250 °C) with liquid CO₂ as freezing agent. The bearing tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM 5961 [32], and the specimens were loaded with a displacement rate of 0.3 mm/min until ultimate failure, in temperature $T = +50$ °C. A voltage generator and an oscilloscope were used for Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) with Lamb waves.

TABLE II. COMPOSITE MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Property	Carbon fibers [38]	Epoxy matrix [39]	Lamina Exp.
Longitudinal modulus E_{11} (MPa)	230000	3200	34433
Transversal modulus E_{22} (MPa)	6000	3200	3610
Through-thickness modulus E_{33} (MPa)	-	3200	3610
Shear modulus G_{12} (MPa)	18000	1300	2421
Shear modulus G_{23} (MPa)	-	1300	2421
Shear modulus G_{13} (MPa)	-	1300	1561
Poisson coefficient ν_{12}	0.36	0.35	0.36
Poisson coefficient ν_{23}	-	0.35	0.45
Poisson coefficient ν_{13}	-	0.35	0.35
Longitudinal CTE α ($10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$)	-0.04	4	2
Transversal CTE α ($10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$)	-	-	44
Through-thickness CTE α ($10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$)	-	-	44
Longitudinal tensile strength $\sigma_{11 \max}^T$ (MPa)	3530	86	253
Longitudinal compression strength $\sigma_{11 \max}^C$ (MPa)	-	-	230
Transversal compression strength $\sigma_{22 \max}^C$ (MPa)	-	-	74
In plane shear strength τ_{12}^{\max} (MPa)	-	-	25
Out plane shear strength τ_{23}^{\max} (MPa)	-	-	37
Out plane shear strength τ_{13}^{\max} (MPa)	-	-	37

TABLE III. ISOTROPIC MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF THE METALLIC PARTS [40]

Property	AA 7075T6	A2-70
Elastic modulus E (MPa)	71016	206000
Shear modulus G (MPa)	26890	75842
Poisson coefficient ν	0.33	0.36
Thermal coefficient CTE α ($10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$)	24	18

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Finite Element Model

A three-dimensional (3D) FEM model, using linear brick 8-node elements, was developed in MSC Nastran for the joint geometry model, as it is shown in Figure 2(a). Each separate part was modeled: aluminum and composite adherents, the washer, and a combined bolt-nut part. The adherents were modeled with in-creased radial mesh density around the hole where high strain gradients exist. Regarding the joint clamping in the testing machine, the boundary conditions imposed on the FE model are presented in Figure 2(a). The displacements u , v , and w are defined along the x, y, and z directions. The boundary conditions represent clamping of the nodes on top and bottom surfaces at the end of the aluminum adherent. They additionally block the translations on y and z directions (v and w) at the rightmost end of the composite adherent. This is only

observed, though, on the surface of the adherent over the length of 70 mm. Each side was gripped during the test to agree with the experiment. The other nodes through the thickness of the lap joint were not blocked in the experimental test or in the simulation. The tabs at the end of the adherents were considered to reciprocally compensate their thickness when gripped. The intention was to induce bending as it may often happen in practice. For simulating the quasi-static loading condition of the testing machine, a prescribed u displacement on the x direction was applied to the nodes from both surfaces of the composite adherent at the rightmost end.

Fig. 2. 3D finite element model: (a) hybrid joint with boundary conditions, (b) contact surfaces marked with red color, (c) countersunk bolt joint assembly.

In order to avoid rigid body motions in FEA analysis, light springs were attached to the not fully constrained components such as the bolt, the washer, and the laminated adherent. For simulating the bolt pre-load due to the applied torque level, a 330 N axial force was applied in the bolt shank, using the pretension section from the Bolt Preload Module of MSC Patran-Nastran. The composite laminated adherent is modeled with continuum solid-shell advanced elements available in MSC Patran-Nastran. These special solid elements have bending properties like shells and one integrating point per element is considered. The finite element model has 6 elements across the laminate thickness, with one solid-shell element per each ply, thus, stress in each ply can be determined and the correct bending-twisting coupling is obtained. The number of elements and nodes for each part of the finite element model is given in Table IV.

TABLE IV. FEM MODEL DESCRIPTION

Part	Elements	Nodes
Composite adherent	3568	3284
Metal adherent	2413	2318
Bolt	862	824
Washer	394	357
Total	7237	6783

In the 3D model, the contact with clearance between the bolt and the surface of the hole is realized as follows. The method requires the definition of the bodies that can come into contact. The contact bodies may be the whole physical bodies

(laminated adherents, bolt, washer). However, it has been shown in [42] that it is more efficient to consider element sets of these physical bodies, as shown in Figure 2(b), because the number of checks for contact between bodies at each iteration of the solution is reduced. The finite element model was refined in the vicinity of the hole so as to better capture the effects of stress concentrators (Figure 2(c)). Therefore, the minimum element length is 0.33 mm around the hole. The minimum element length is increasing from hole towards the clamped ends of the adherents. Another step in defining nonlinear contact phenomena is the choice between the discrete contact and the analytical contact. When a node on a solid reaches the contact segment on the other contact body, the node is constrained on this segment with respect to the normal of this segment. In the case of discrete contact for normal detection, the linear representation with the finite elements of the contact surface is used, which leads to the calculation of each element normal. If the surface is not planar, then when a node touches the contact segment it is blocked between two different normal elements due to their discontinuity, and is shifted and constrained on the contact segment. This impediment has an adverse effect on the quality [42]. In the case of analytical contact, a smooth Coons surface is constructed through the nodes of the solid contact segment. Later, this analytical surface is used to calculate the normal of the contact surface between the two solids, thus solving the problem of node blocking due to the discontinuity of the surface normal between the bodies. This method leads to a better representation of the joint geometry. Especially, its deformation and the accuracy of the numerical results are far superior to those of the discrete contact technique. Consequently, the former method was applied in this work.

B. Model Validation

In this section, the results generated from the tests are compared with the ones of the 3D FEM. Strains in the selected points on the surface of the laminated adherent were used to check the model accuracy. On the composite adherent, strain gauges were applied, and the joint was loaded in tension to a level that prevents any important damage of the composite adherent (1.2 kN load) at $T_1 = +50$ °C. Figure 3 depicts the locations of the 3 mm length strain gauges, type 1-Ly16-3/350, with 350 Ω electrical resistance, fabricated by HBM. Gauges 1, 3, and 4 were aligned with the loading direction and were located on the bottom surface of the laminate adherent, except gauge number 2. This was located in the shear plane on the composite adherent top surface in the same location but opposite to gauge number 1. The numerically calculated and experimentally measured strains are given in Table V and Figure 4. The notations in Figure 4 are: Exp. curves denote the variation of experimentally acquired strains and FEM the numerical ones. From Table V, it is clearly shown that strain gauges 1 and 2 indicate a joint bending, although the loading is a tensile one. The strain readings for gauges 3 and 4 are somehow different, indicating a misalignment effect of the joint along the longitudinal axis, which is the loading x axis. As a conclusion, it can be considered that the model has quite satisfactorily predicted the joint linear behavior, and can be further used in temperature parametric studies for the linear response of the hybrid aluminum-composite joint.

Fig. 3. Strain gauge locations, all dimensions in mm.

TABLE V. EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STRAIN READINGS FOR 1.2 KN APPLIED LOAD

Gauge number	Experimental (Exp.) strain (µm/m)	Numerical (FEM) strain (µm/m)
1	776	810
2	-1300	-1252
3	757	689
4	679	615

Fig. 4. Experimental and numerical surface strains.

The results of the acoustic simulations highlighted once more that the position of the resonators influences both the acting frequency of the resonators and their effectiveness, leading to a reduction of the attenuation (Figure 8).

C. Nonlinear Shear Deformation

In order to take into account the nonlinear behavior of the composite adherend within the hybrid metal-composite joint, the simulation must account for the two most important nonlinear mechanisms: lamina nonlinear shear deformations and stiffness reduction due to damage accumulation at the lamina level. These two nonlinearities are considered by using an external user-defined subroutine named User_mat, edited in FORTRAN. User_mat calls the modified predefined MSC Nastran subroutine UMAT in order to implement the material nonlinearities specified above. Authors in [44] developed the in plane nonlinear shear stress-strain constitutive model at the lamina level, utilizing the high order elasticity theory.

D. Failure Criteria and Continuous Degradation Rules

The most dominant micro-failure modes for bearing joints are matrix compression, fiber compression and fiber-matrix shear modes. In [45], failure criteria for unidirectional laminates are used in the PDA of the laminated adherent around the hole, as the failure indexes are calculated with relation (1) for matrix compression and (2) for fibers compression-shear damages:

$$FI_1 = \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{22,max}^c}{2\tau_{23}^c} \right) - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{\sigma_{22,max}^c} + \frac{(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)^2}{4(\tau_{23}^c)^2} - \frac{\sigma_2 \cdot \sigma_3}{(\tau_{23}^c)^2} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12,max}^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{\tau_{13,max}^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{23}}{\tau_{23,max}^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{11,max}^T} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

$$FI_2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_{11,max}^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12,max}^c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{13}}{\tau_{13,max}^c} \right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

E. Continuous Degradation Rules for Longitudinal Moduli

A strain based degradation rule is proposed for the reduction of E_{ii} ($i = 1...3$), as described in [45]. The fiber or matrix damage initiates at a user-defined strain ϵ_{ii}^{init} , while the stiffness reduction is performed by:

$$E_{ii}^{t+\Delta t} = \begin{cases} E_{ii}^0 \cdot \left(1 - d_i \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{ii}^{t+\Delta t} - \epsilon_{ii}^{init}}{\Delta \epsilon_{ii}} \right) & \text{for } \epsilon_{ii}^{init} \leq \epsilon_{ii}^{t+\Delta t} \leq \epsilon_{ii}^{init} + \Delta \epsilon_{ii} \\ E_{ii}^0 \cdot (1 - d_i) \cdot \frac{\epsilon_{ii}^{init} + \Delta \epsilon_{ii}}{\epsilon_{ii}^{t+\Delta t}} & \text{for } \epsilon_{ii}^{t+\Delta t} \geq \epsilon_{ii}^{init} + \Delta \epsilon_{ii} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where E_{ii}^0 is the initial modulus of elasticity from Table I in the lamina on-axis system, $\Delta \epsilon_{ii}$ is a user-defined strain step to ensure a smooth reduction of the properties upon failure, and d_i is the reduction factor. Initial damage strain and corresponding stress ϵ_{ii}^{init} are determined by simulation for $FI = 1$, with $FI = \max(FI_1, FI_2)$. A representation of the moduli of elasticity decrease with the reduction factor is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Stiffness reduction due to damage with a reduction factor d_i .

The reduction parameters for E_{ii} ($i = 1...3$) obtained after several parameter tuning FEA iterations are presented in Table VI.

F. Continuous Degradation Rules for Shear Moduli

In post failure analysis, the in-plane shear moduli G_{ij} are reduced using the maximum shear strains $\gamma_{ij}^{t+\Delta t}$ for $FI > 1$, according to [45]:

$$G_{ij} = G_{ij}^0 \left(0.1 + 0.9 \cdot \frac{\gamma_{ij}^{\text{init}}}{\gamma_{ij}^{\text{t}+\Delta t}} \right), \quad i \neq j = 1,2,3 \quad (4)$$

TABLE VI. DEGRADATION PARAMETERS FOR LONGITUDINAL MODULI

Failure mode	d_i	ΔE_{ii}
Fiber shear-compression ($i = 1$)	0.45	0.01
Matrix compression ($i = 2,3$)	0.57	0.01

G. Poisson Coefficients Reduction

Reduction of Poisson ratios is proposed in order to comply with the elastic stability of the orthotropic materials, as suggested in [19]:

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{12} &= \nu_{12}^0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_{11}E_{22}^0}{E_{22}E_{11}^0}} \\ \nu_{13} &= \nu_{13}^0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_{11}E_{33}^0}{E_{33}E_{11}^0}} \\ \nu_{23} &= \nu_{23}^0 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{E_{22}E_{33}^0}{E_{33}E_{22}^0}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

These conditions are imposed as normal stiffness ratios may vary significantly with degradation. Simultaneously, the material’s stress-strain matrix has to be maintained positive, and thus allow the FE solver to perform calculations. Assuming constant product of the major Poisson’s ratios before and after reduction (degradation) as $\nu_{ij} \cdot \nu_{ji} = \nu_{ij}^0 \cdot \nu_{ji}^0$ and that $\nu_{ij}/\nu_{ji} = E_{ii}/E_{jj}$, relations (5) are resulting.

H. Simulation Results

The comparison between experimental and numerical results in terms of the geometry parameters (width/hole diameter- b/D , and edge distance/hole diameter- e/D ratios) effects on damage initiation and progressive failure mechanisms are presented below. Load-displacement curves are shown in Figure 6. From Figure 6 (experimental curves), it can be observed that the friction static force between the aluminum and composite adherents is approximately $F_f = 150$ N. Considering the adherents clamping force $P = 330$ N, it is implied that the real friction coefficient should be equal to $\mu = F_f/2P = 150/2 \cdot 330 = 0.227$. This value is quite close to the value used in numerical simulation, $\mu = 0.235$ [43], which suggests that the simulation considered the friction base phenomena with satisfying accuracy. The small difference between the friction coefficient values may be caused by the fact that during the experiments of this study the surfaces of the two adherents were not properly cleaned with the ultrasonic technique as in [43]. However, in the numerical simulation, the constant force indicating friction is not obtained as in the experiment. By comparing the plots, we can see that the increase of geometric parameters has augmented more than twice the force at the limit of linear behavior of the joint (deviation from linearity, point A) and maximum load (point B). At point A on the load-displacement curves, the fiber and matrix compression damage onset around the hole obtained experimentally is evident according to Figure 7. Point A represents the first damage initiation point, denoting the limit load of the joint, and is located at the major deviation of the force-displacement curves from linear behavior. At this point, the compression fiber damage appeared as an indicator of the

bearing failure initiation, despite the fact that the fiber-matrix shear damage is also observed in that point. Matrix compression damage is also present at point A but this does not contribute a lot to the joint stiffness loss, as already mentioned, because carbon fibers have the most important role in joint stiffening. The main interests of this study aim towards applications in the aerospace industry, and being on the conservative side, we consider that the limit load is obtained for point A. Beyond this point it is safer to consider that a post failure scenario appears, although the ultimate load is reached in point B. For aerospace joints (whose strength was not proven by limit and ultimate load tests), the approach is very conservative, especially if data are not available or experimental testing is missing, and an additional fitting factor of 1.15 is added to the safety factor of 1.5. So, to cover the uncertainties and to avoid any incidental failures the combined factor of safety becomes 1.725. We prefer to be on the safe side of first-ply failure in our analysis and to consider post failure beyond point A.

Fig. 6. Load-displacement behavior.

Fig. 7. Force-displacement curves. Geometry Case 1.

As can be seen from Figure 8, in 0° plies, fiber damage is more predominant than matrix damage, while in 90° plies, the two micro level damages have almost the same spread out. In Figures 8-11, the dark blue color represents undamaged elements, while the red color states the $E_{ii}^0(1-d_i)$ residual stiffness of the elements. In Figure 8, it can be observed that the damaged layer is located to the top surface of the laminate,

taking into account that the laminate plate was modeled with only one element per each ply in the thickness direction. The first ply failure position could be affected by the bolt tilting in the hole due to the exiting joint clearance and secondary bending effect.

can be easily observed in Figures 7-11. In point B, post failure has been completely developed, and maximum force is reached.

Fig. 8. Bearing damage onset for Case 1: (a) point A, (b) point B.

I. Experimental Results

In Figure 7, point B represents the joint ultimate failure, as explained above. After point A, the damage accumulation determines gradual joint stiffness reduction, and the characteristic curve becomes nonlinear. From point A to point B, the post failure stage is completely developed where the residual stiffness is continuously reduced. On this stage, the fiber compression, matrix compression, and fiber-matrix shear damage are increasing at the bearing plane through the whole thickness of the laminate plate, as it can be seen in Figure 9. Point C (Figure 7) represents the catastrophic final failure of the joint when fiber compression, matrix compression, and fiber-matrix shear damages start, and propagate on approximately +/- 45° from the loading direction. At this point, they are extended to a large portion of the laminate plate on the bearing plane through free edge behind the laminate hole, as it

Fig. 9. The geometry influence on the joint failure modes: (a) point C, FEM, Case 1, (b) point C, EXP, all cases.

A summary of the geometry parameter effects on the progressive failure of the metal-composite hybrid joints is presented in Table VII and Figure 12. In Table VII, F_{LL} and F_{UL} represent the *limit* and *ultimate* forces of the joint to axial quasi-static tensile loading, and are corresponding to the A and B points from the characteristic force-displacement curves discussed above. In Table VII, it is clearly seen that bearing failure mode appears for all values of b/D as the joint was designed in accordance with ASTM standard [17] to induce bearing failure. It is also noticed, though, that for $e/D < 4$, shear-out failure mode is present despite the fact that literature research recommends $e/D < 3$ for this type of failure mode. In Figure 12 the influence of the geometric parameter b/D on the joint ultimate failure load is illustrated. It can be seen that the curve has an asymptotic value of 2200 N for the ultimate failure load, which denotes that values $b/D > 10$ are not recommended because they have no more effects on the joint failure load.

Fig. 10. Catastrophic failure in point C for Case 2: (a) stiffness reduction at catastrophic failure, (b) bearing failure of the composite adherent.

Fig. 11. Catastrophic failure in point C for Case 3: (a) stiffness reduction at catastrophic failure, (b) net section and secondary bending of the composite adherent.

TABLE VII. GEOMETRY EFFECTS ON MACROSCOPIC FAILURE MODES OF THE JOINTS

Geometry	T [°C]	Torque [Nm]	F_{LL} [N]		F_{UL} [N]		Failure mode
			EXP	FEM	EXP	FEM	
$b/D=6.8$ $e/D=2$	+50	0.5	1317.43	1376.65	1480.32	1548.94	Bearing/s hear-out
$b/D=8.4$ $e/D=3$			1246.07	1225.65	2044.20	2043.94	Bearing/s hear-out
$b/D=10$ $e/D=4$			1448.37	1500.03	2173.78	2151.84	Bearing

Fig. 12. The influence of b/D on joint ultimate failure load.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the effects of the geometry parameters width/hole diameter- b/D and edge distance/hole diameter- e/D ratios on the stiffness, damage initiation, and progressive failure for single-lap, single-bolt, hybrid metal-composite joints are investigated, using both strain gauge measurements and finite element analysis. The countersunk bolt was chosen, as it determines a complex tridimensional state of stress around the hole, and thus a complex mode of failure in the composite adherent. A 3D FEM model, which incorporates geometrical and friction contact full nonlinearities, was developed in the MSC Patran-Nastran commercial software for predicting the joint stiffness and strength. The PDA material model was implemented with the help of a user-defined subroutine, named User_mat in FORTRAN.

The simulation results were in good agreement with the experiments in terms of load-displacement behavior, surface strain, joint stiffness, and limit and ultimate loads. This denoted that the 3D FEM model, including full nonlinearities and an explicit solver, is quite accurate, and can predict the metal-composite mechanical behavior of the joint in both linear elastic and nonlinear elastic ranges, including bearing, shear-out, and net-section failure modes.

The simulation results were in good agreement with the experiments in terms of surface strains, load-displacement behavior, FPF (First Ply Failure), and ultimate failure loads. This denoted that the 3D FEM model including full nonlinearities and explicit solver are quite accurate, and can predict the metal-composite joint's mechanical behavior on both linear-elastic and nonlinear elastic ranges, including the failure modes as bearing and shear-out. Regarding the geometry effects on the load-displacement curves, it can be seen that loading joint behavior released some interesting features at the beginning stage due to friction between the plates (Figure 6). This friction stage consists of static and dynamic friction. From the graphs, the friction load can be detected and, knowing the clamping force from the torque level, the friction coefficient between the plates can be calculated.

From the numerical and experimental results, it can be deduced that when the geometry parameters (b/D , e/D)

increase, the ultimate failure loads increase up to an asymptotic value of 2200 N, denoting that the geometry parameters have a limited effect upon the strength of the joint.

All the failure modes appeared in the composite counter part of the joint, and thus the geometry parameters of the joint were selected accordingly.

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Optimal FLC-Sugeno Controller based on PSO for an Active Damping System

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a method for the design of an optimal Sugeno model (FLC-Sugeno) fuzzy logic controller for the active suspension system of quarter-vehicle models is presented. The parameters of the FLC-Sugeno controller are optimally searched, using the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm. The 16 optimized parameters include 3 parameters for adjusting the domain of the input state variables and control variables at the controller's output, 4 fuzzy set adjustment numbers of the linguistic variables, and 9 parameters as the fuzzy rule weights of the rule system control. To compare and evaluate the effectiveness of the optimal FLC-Sugeno controller, an optimal PID controller using PSO is also implemented. Simulation results of the active damping system with the controllers when affected by the same type and standard road surface excitation show that the FLC-Sugeno controller is optimal for the quick ending of the oscillations of vehicle body displacement. The result shows that the proposed controlling scheme can be extended and applied to more complex active damping system models.

Keywords-FLC-Sugeno; particle swarm optimization; active suspension system; quarter-vehicle models

I. INTRODUCTION

Considering quarter-vehicle models, the active damping controlling model has the best quality but a complex structure because it involves an additional controller for the damper. Different algorithms give highly divergent control efficiency values. Selecting and designing a controller according to the optimal algorithm is the goal of the research on the active damper model. The active damping system, in addition to the spring mechanism and the soft damping element, also involves a component that generates electromagnetic force from the electric motor with the purpose to quickly extinguish the oscillation process in the vertical direction of the system, or in other words, minimize the road surface impact on the vehicle body.

Many scientists have researched the application of fuzzy controllers in damping systems [1-7]. Active suspension of cars, using fuzzy logic controller, optimized by the genetic algorithm (GA), was proposed in [1]. The authors performed membership function adjustment utilizing GA. The limitation was that they stopped when the membership function was

optimized, and did not optimize the other parameters of the controller. Today there are many studies showing that there are many optimization algorithms superior to GA, such as the PSO employed in the current study. Many studies evaluated the effectiveness of Fuzzy Logic Control (FLC) and compared its results to the ones of PID controller, which provides effective control in a narrow working area [3]. The PID controller can also have its coefficients adjusted by a fuzzy set to form an adaptive fuzzy PID controller [8-10]. However, the controller structure is often complex. The FLC is widely researched, and applied in active damping systems [11-14].

A common feature of previous studies when applying FLC controller to damping systems in general is the design of fuzzy controllers without optimizing the controller parameters or utilizing the outdated optimization algorithm GA to ameliorate the membership function of the fuzzy set [1]. To overcome this limitation, in this study the proposed solution is to design the FLC-Sugeno controller that optimizes at the same time the fuzzy set of the membership functions and the weights of the rule system. The optimal technique considered is PSO [16, 17].

II. DAMPING SYSTEM MODELS

A. The Active Damping System Model

The active suspension system quarter-vehicle model is presented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The active suspension system quarter-vehicle model.

In Figure 1, the lower body block m_w represents the tires, wheels, brakes, and components in the wheel that act on the system, m_c represents a quarter of a vehicle's mass including passengers and payload. The tire is characterized by the stiffness parameter c_w and the damping coefficient d_w . The upper and lower body blocks are linked by spring mechanism c_c , damping mechanism d_c , and electromagnetic force generating mechanism F_e . Let the displacements of road surface, lower body block, upper body block be x_g, x_w, x_c . The Linear Brushless Permanent Magnet (LBP) motor creates force F_e with the purpose of minimizing the vibration of the system or the impact of the road surface x_g on the upper body mass. Thus, the system includes two inputs: the noise from the road surface x_g and the force F_e . The output of the system consists of x_c and x_w , the purpose of the control process is $x_c \rightarrow 0$. The following differential equation system describes the system:

$$\begin{aligned} m_c \ddot{x}_c &= -c_c(x_c - x_w) - d_c(t)(\dot{x}_c - \dot{x}_w) + F_e(t) \\ m_w \ddot{x}_w &= c_c(x_c - x_w) + d_c(t)(\dot{x}_c - \dot{x}_w) \\ &\quad - c_w(t)(x_w - x_g) + d_w(t)(\dot{x}_w - \dot{x}_g) - F_e(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

According to [18], the damper spring c_c is chosen because it behaves linearly within the working range, assuming c_c is a constant. The coefficients $d_c(t)$, $c_w(t)$, and $d_w(t)$ change in a small range around the working point location.

$$\begin{aligned} d_c(t) &= d_{c0} + \Delta d_c; \quad c_w(t) = \\ c_{w0} + \Delta c_w; \quad d_w(t) &= d_{w0} + \Delta d_w \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where d_{c0}, c_{w0}, d_{w0} are the values at the working point and $\Delta d_c, \Delta c_w, \Delta d_w$ are their value changes around the working point.

B. Linear Brushless Permanent Magnet Motor Model

The structure of the LBM is shown in Figure 2 with the following assumptions: The inductance of the motor's stator coils is constant, the rotor l is infinite to ignore terminal effects, the magnetic flux intensity of the magnet is constant, and the

magnetic saturation effect is ignored [20]. The LBM model is written in the form of dq coordinates as:

$$\begin{cases} u_d = R_s i_d + \frac{d\Psi_d}{dt} - \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{\pi}{\tau_p} \Psi_q; & u_q = R_s i_q + \frac{d\Psi_q}{dt} - \frac{dx}{dt} \frac{\pi}{\tau_p} \Psi_d \\ F_e = \frac{\pi}{\tau_p} \Psi_m i_q; & F_e - (K_d \frac{dx}{dt} + K_e + F_t) = I \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where u_d, u_q, i_d , and i_q are the voltage and current on stator, R_s is the stator resistance, Ψ_d and Ψ_q represent the magnetic flux on the d and q axes, F_e is the electromagnetic force, I is the inertial force of the motor shaft, x is the distance movement of the motor shaft, K_d and K_e are the dynamic resistance and static resistance coefficients, and F_t is the external resistance force.

Fig. 2. Structure of the linear brushless permanent magnet motor.

C. The Model of Active Damping System using LBM

Substituting (2) into (1), we get the system of differential equations describing the damping system:

$$\begin{aligned} m_c \ddot{x}_c &= -c_c(x_c - x_w) - \\ &\quad (d_{c0} + \Delta d_c)(\dot{x}_c - \dot{x}_w) + F_e(t) \\ m_w \ddot{x}_w &= c_c(x_c - x_w) + (d_{c0} + \Delta d_c)(\dot{x}_c - \dot{x}_w) \\ &\quad - (c_{w0} + \Delta c_w)(x_w - x_g) + \\ &\quad (d_{w0} + \Delta d_w)(\dot{x}_w - \dot{x}_g) - F_e(t) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The state variables are set as:

$$\underline{x} = [x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3 \ x_4]^T = [(x_c - x_w) \ \dot{x}_c \ (x_w - x_g) \ \dot{x}_w]^T \quad (5)$$

The output variable y is:

$$y = [\ddot{x}_c \quad F \quad (x_c - x_w)]^T \quad (6)$$

where F is the dynamic load force created by the wheel:

$$F = (c_{w0} + \Delta c_w)(x_g - x_w) + (d_{w0} + \Delta d_w)(\dot{x}_g - \dot{x}_w) \quad (7)$$

From this way of setting the state variable, we bring (4) to the system of state equations:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\underline{x}} = A \underline{x} + B F + \Delta \underline{x} + N \dot{x}_g \\ y = C \underline{x} + D F + M \dot{x}_g \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

With the matrices:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -\frac{c_c}{m_c} & -\frac{d_{c0}}{m_c} & 0 & \frac{d_{c0}}{m_c} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{c_c}{m_w} & \frac{d_{c0}}{m_w} & \frac{c_c}{m_w} & \frac{d_{w0} + d_{w0}}{m_w} \end{bmatrix}; \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{m_c} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{1}{m_w} \end{bmatrix}; \quad N = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -1 \\ \frac{d_{w0}}{m_w} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta d_{c0}}{m_c} & 0 & \frac{\Delta d_{c0}}{m_c} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & \frac{\Delta d_{w0}}{m_w} & -\frac{\Delta c_c}{m_w} & -\frac{\Delta d_{w0}}{m_w} \end{bmatrix}; D = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{m_c} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{c_c}{m_c} & -\frac{d_c}{m_c} & 0 & \frac{d_c}{m_c} \\ 0 & 0 & -c_w & -d_w \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; M = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ d_{c0} + \Delta d_{w0} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

III. THE PROPOSED NEW OPTIMAL CONTROLLER FOR ACTIVE DAMPING SYSTEMS

With the purpose of minimizing the impact of road surface noise on the upper body, which means reducing the amplitude x_c to 0 in the shortest time, we propose an output feedback controller as shown in Figure 3. The Electric motor block includes a linear motor, a current controller, and a conversion block to the dq system. The suspension system damper block is influenced by road surface noise $x_g(t)$, and receives the impact force F_e from the Electric motor block.

A. Design of the FLC Controller Structure

The fuzzy logic controller is selected according to the Sugeno model. It includes two inputs, e and ce and one output, u . The fuzzy sets for input/output linguistic variables are:

- Input variables: e, ce include 5 triangular fuzzy sets NB, N, ZE, PS, PB defined in the domain $[-1, 1]$. The fuzzy sets are designed as strong fuzzy partitions, which means that for any real value x , the total membership of x in the fuzzy sets is equal to 1.
- The output variable u consists of 7 singleton fuzzy sets, NB, N, NS, ZE, PS, P, PB defined in the domain $[-1, 1]$.

Fig. 3. The proposed active suspension system quarter-vehicle model.

The FLC-Sugeno controller is designed with the value domain of input/output variables normalized on the interval $[-1, 1]$. When coupled to the system, the coefficient K_e, K_{ce} , and K_u will correct their values to the real domain of the signal. In this way, we can flexibly combine the FLC-Sugeno controller into different control systems. The simulation blocks of the control system are shown in Figures 4 – 8.

Fig. 4. Simulation diagram of the active damping system using the FLC-Sugeno controller.

Fig. 5. The structure of the motor control block.

Fig. 6. The structure of the dq to abc block.

Fig. 7. The linear brushless permanent magnet motor model.

The motor control block includes two current control loops. The i_d current has a fixed set value, while the i_q current receives its set value from the PID F_e controller. The DQ-ABC block receives signals u_d, u_q through the dq coordinate conversion to control the linear motor. The motor creates the electromagnetic force F_e that participates in the oscillation process of the damping system built on (8).

Fig. 8. The damping system model.

B. Optimizing Controller Parameters with PSO

The PSO optimization algorithm [17] is a random search algorithm based on simulating the behavior and interaction of birds when searching for food sources. Each individual (or element) in the swarm is characterized by two components, the displacement velocity vector v_i and the position vector x_i . Each element in the swarm has a *fitness value*, which is evaluated by the *fitness function*. The objective function of the optimization process is chosen as the IAE (Integral of the Absolute magnitude of the Error):

$$fitness = IAE = \sum_{n=1}^j |e(n)| \rightarrow \min \tag{9}$$

The optimal diagram of the fuzzy controller is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Optimal diagram of the FLC controller using PSO.

1) Fuzzy Set Optimization

The diagram that optimizes the parameters of the FLC using the PSO algorithm is shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Optimal fuzzy sets based on PSO.

To find the optimal fuzzy set shape, we limit the following conditions:

- The fuzzy set ZE is an isosceles triangle with a vertex at 0.
- Fuzzy sets PB and NB are symmetric at point 0. Correspondingly, we have other symmetric fuzzy sets at point 0 (N, P), (NS, PS).

Regarding the upper limit, by determining the fuzzy sets with symmetry for the optimal controller, our goal is to find the parameters $\alpha_e, \alpha_{ce}, \alpha_u,$ and β_u . The search domain for these parameters is chosen in the range: $\alpha_e, \alpha_{ce} \in [0.2, 0.75]$; $\beta_u \in [0.25, 0.5]$; $\alpha_u \in [0.5, 0.75]$.

2) Optimizing the Weights of Fuzzy Rules

Each control rule carries a weight that determines the level of reliability of that rule. Most scientists only focus on researching the fuzzy set design and determining the rule system without paying attention to the weight of the rules. In this study, we use the PSO algorithm to find the weight of each rule. The control rule system and the weight of each rule is shown in Table I. We have 25 rules with w_i ($i=1, 9$) being the weight of each rule. We acquired 9 weights for 25 rules because it was discovered that, according to the nature of this control system, the rule system is symmetrical considering the center of the rule table, so rules in symmetrical positions will have equal weight. Specifically, the rule “if $e=NB$ and $ce=NB$ then $u=NB$ ” and rule “if $e=PB$ and $ce=PB$ then $u=PB$ ” have the same weight w_1 , rules “if $e=NB$ and $ce=NS$ then $u=NB$ ” and “if $e=PB$ and $ce=PS$ then $u=PB$ ” have the same weight w_2 , etc. With that symmetric property, we can reduce the number of variables that need to be optimized from 25 to 9.

TABLE I. CONTROL SYSTEM WITH WEIGHTS

$e \backslash ce$	NB	NS	ZE	PS	PB
NB	NB w_1	NB w_2	N w_3	NS w_4	ZE w_5
NS	NB w_4	N w_5	NS w_6	ZE w_7	PS w_8
ZE	N w_7	NS w_8	ZE w_9	PS w_8	P w_7
PS	NS w_8	ZE w_7	PS w_6	P w_5	PB w_4
PB	ZE w_5	PS w_4	P w_3	PB w_2	PB w_1

Fig. 11. Optimization flow chart based on PSO.

Thus, to design the proposed optimal FLC-Sugeno controller, the PSO algorithm will search for 16 parameters:

- 3 correction parameters $K_e, K_{ce},$ and K_u .

- 4 fuzzy set parameters α_e , α_{ce} , α_u , and β_u .
- 9 weights of the control rule system (w_i).

The optimal algorithm flow chart is shown in Figure 11. We used the function `particleswarm()` from the MATLAB/Simulink toolbox. This function supports the optimization algorithm PSO.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulated system was built, and the received physical parameters of the model are shown in Table II. The parameters of the linear motor are given in Table III.

TABLE II. DAMPER MODEL PHYSICAL PARAMETERS

Symbol	Value
m_c	256 kg
m_w	31 kg
c_{c0}	20200 N/m
Δc_c	1010 N/m
d_{c0}	1140 Ns/m
Δd_c	57 Ns/m
c_{w0}	128000 N/m
Δc_w	1280 N/m
d_{w0}	0 Ns/m

TABLE III. LINEAR MOTOR PARAMETERS

Symbol	Value
R_s	0.2 Ω
L_s	8.5 mH
M_s	2 mH
τ_p	10 mm
Ψ_m	10 mH
F_t	10N
R_{abc}	0.2 Ω
L_{abc}	8.5 mH
Ψ_{abc}	2 mH
I	10
K_d	50 N
K_e	5N

After running the optimization, we get the results shown in Table IV. To evaluate the control efficiency of the optimal FLC-Sugeno set, we additionally designed an optimal PID controller with parameters K_P , K_I , and K_D also optimized by PSO.

TABLE IV. OPTIMAL PARAMETER VALUES OF FLC-SUGENO

Fuzzy set parameters	Weight of the rule system
$\alpha_e = 0.398389$	$w_1 = 0.198813$
$\alpha_{ce} = 0.625307$	$w_2 = 0.257075$
$\alpha_u = 0.636611$	$w_3 = 0.0747781$
$\beta_u = 0.406224$	$w_4 = 1$
Parameters for adjusting the domain of variables	$w_5 = 0.337037$
$K_e = 0.3$	$w_6 = 0.723424$
$K_{ce} = 0.289315$	$w_7 = 0.905881$
$K_u = 4101.68$	$w_8 = 0.868694$
	$w_9 = 0.125044$

The simulation scenario is set up with a total simulation time of 5.5 s. On 0.5 s, step excitation with amplitude 0.3 is applied. On 3 s, step stimulation with amplitude -0.3 is added.

The simulation results of the active damping system subjected to the ISO standard excitation with optimal controllers are shown in Figure 12. On 0.5 s, when the road surface stimulus is introduced into the system, the blue line is the vehicle body displacement response without control. It takes 3 oscillation cycles to reach stable value. The maximum magnitude of vehicle body displacement without control is 15.5% larger than with optimal PID control. Meanwhile, with the optimal PID controller (yellow line), a stable value is reached after only 2 control cycles, but the switching amplitude is still quite large. The red line is the vehicle body displacement response with the proposed optimal FLC-Sugeno controller. It can be clearly seen that the response still has many oscillation peaks, but the transition amplitude is greatly reduced. At 3 s, a stimulus equal to -0.3 is applied to the system. the responses have the same appearance and trend as those applied at 0.5 s.

Fig. 12. Response of the active damping system with excitation and optimal controllers.

The results of this study show that the vehicle body motion amplitude is much reduced compared to the results in [2].

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an optimal fuzzy controller according to the Sugeno model was proposed. The parameters of the controller were optimized with the the PSO algorithm in terms of fuzzy set and weighting rules. This optimal fuzzy controller is applied to the active damping system according to the quarter-vehicle model. The simulation results showed the efficiency of the optimal fuzzy controller.

Through the above findings, it can be seen that the optimal FLC-Sugeno controller responds well in highly nonlinear damping systems. When optimized with PSO, the FLC-Sugeno gives much better control response than the PID controller. The research results indicate that when performing overall optimization of both membership functions of fuzzy sets and fuzzy rule weights using PSO, the optimal FLC-Sugeno works very well. From here, the control design can be applied to more complex models such as the 1/2 model or the overall model of an entire vehicle.

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Comparative Analysis of Machine Learning Algorithms for Investigating Myocardial Infarction Complications

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ABSTRACT

Myocardial Infarction (MI) is a condition often leading to death. It arises from inadequate blood flow to the heart, therefore, the classification of MI complications contributing to lethal outcomes is essential to save lives. Machine learning algorithms provide solutions to support the categorization of the MI complication attributes and predict lethal results. This paper compares various machine learning algorithms to classify myocardial infarction complications and to predict fatal consequences. The considered algorithms are Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Naive Bayes (NB), and Decision Tree (DT). The main objective of this paper is to compare these algorithms in two scenarios: initially using the full dataset once and then using the dataset again, after implementing the WEKA attribute selection algorithm. To accomplish this goal, data from the Krasnoyarsk Interdistrict Clinical Hospital were employed. Results in general revealed that the MLP classifier demonstrated optimal performance regarding the full MI data, whereas the DT classifier emerged as more favorable when the dataset sample size was diminished through an attribute selection algorithm.

Keywords-data mining; classification; multilayer perceptron; Naive Bayes; decision tree; prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

When the blood supply to a myocardium section is diminished or halted, it frequently results in Myocardial

Infarction (MI), which can subsequently cause circulatory decline and abrupt death. This study centers around examining MI complications through data gathered at the Krasnoyarsk Interdistrict Clinical Hospital in Russia [1]. The primary aim of

this data selection was to investigate the MI complications that contribute to lethal outcomes. Consequently, one suggestion is to extract insights from these complication records for determining the key attributes directly influencing the lethal outcomes. It is crucial to classify MI complications and predict lethal consequences in order for necessary measures to be taken to decrease the condition prevalence. Machine learning algorithms offer potential solutions for classifying complication attributes that may result in death due to MI and for predicting the lethal outcomes. This study focusses on the three machine learning algorithms, Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP), Naive Bayes (NB), and Decision Tree (DT).

In closely related work, machine learning algorithms have been increasingly utilized in the cardiology field. For instance, authors in [2] compared the use of DT and NB for modeling cardiovascular disease. The dataset they used contains 299 patients with 13 attributes. Their results showed that both DT and NB offer high accuracy. Authors in [3] analyzed DT, NB, and Neural Networks (NNs) to design a predictive model for heart disease data containing 336 patients with 24 attributes. They found that all algorithms provided superior performance. Authors in [4] compared Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Logistic Regression (LR) algorithms for performing myocardial infarction prediction, employing a dataset based on 303 patients with 14 attributes. Their findings yielded that LR outperformed the other classifiers. Other studies regarding the use of using machine learning algorithms in cardiology can be found in [5-7]. This paper, however, aims to compare the performance of the MLP, NB, and DT classifiers in two scenarios: using the full dataset of MI complications once and utilizing the same dataset again, after implementing the WEKA attribute selection algorithm. The classifiers are applied to build a classification model for the MI complications in order to predict lethal outcomes. These classifiers were chosen due to their robust theoretical foundations, spanning various schools of thought. The WEKA attribute selection technique [8] is applied to identify the most relevant to fatal outcomes attributes.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Multilayer Perceptron

The MLP algorithm basically is a class of feed-forward Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) that consist of several layers working together to process input data, and produce an output for various applications like pattern recognition, classification, and prediction tasks [9-11].

B. Naive Bayes

The NB algorithm is a widely recognized probabilistic classifier that fundamentally utilizes the probability concept. Its primary function is to address classification issues in a straightforward and efficient manner. By applying Bayes' theorem principles, the algorithm learns the probability of individual objects, their features and the groups to which these features belong [12-14].

C. Decision Tree

The DT algorithm is a classification method for modeling the decision-making process by constructing a tree structure based on specific characteristics of the dataset being analyzed [13-15]. It serves as a tree-diagram-based technique, featuring a root node at the top and leaf nodes at the bottom. Each leaf node possesses a target class attribute.

D. Data Description

The data were amassed via a survey study carried out at the Krasnoyarsk Interdistrict Clinical Hospital in Russia, and are currently accessible through the UCI machine learning repository [1]. Comprised of multivariate characteristics, the dataset includes 1700 patients with 123 attributes. Among these attributes, 111 served as input features, while 12 were considered complications. Nine of these 111 input features were assessed before the conclusion of days one, two, and three, while 102 input features were evaluated upon admission to the hospital. This database primary aim was to explore MI complications in the patient population. Chronic heart failure patients displayed the highest rate (23.18%) of complications, whereas supraventricular tachycardia-afflicted patients exhibited the lowest rate (1.18%). The results due to MI complications were categorized as a diverse outcome (1429 alive cases and with 271 dead cases). The major death causes were identified within 7 categories: Cardiogenic shock, pulmonary edema, myocardial rupture, progression of congestive heart failure, thromboembolism, systole, and ventricular fibrillation. Utilizing the previously mentioned machine learning algorithms, this study primarily concentrates on classifying MI complications and predicting lethal outcomes.

E. Pre-processing Stage

Like other big data, the myocardial infarction data used in this study suffer from some common irregularities that may be found in any real-world database. The pre-processing phase addresses these issues, rendering the data suitable for subsequent classification and prediction tasks. Patient IDs have been eliminated from the analytical process due to their irrelevance in the analysis. Additionally, attributes not directly connected to predicting lethal outcomes, such as the recurrence of pain post-hospital admission, have been excluded. Approximately 8% of the remaining dataset contains missing information. To avoid biased results in predictive modeling caused by missing data, the Multiple Imputation (MI) technique is employed via the MICE function [16], proving to be more effective than conventional methods like complete and available case techniques. The 3 classifiers were applied to the myocardial infarction data in 2 scenarios: using the full dataset once, and using the dataset again, after implementing the WEKA attribute selection algorithm. Sixteen attributes, which included the lethal outcome, were selected after applying the WEKA algorithm. These attributes primarily relate to complications and input features measured at the time of hospital admission. The selected attributes exhibiting a strong correlation with lethal outcomes are presented in Table I:

TABLE I. SELECTED ATTRIBUTES AFTER WEKA

Features measured at the time of admission	Complications
Age	Ventricular fibrillation
Quantity of MIs in the anamnesis	Myocardial rupture
Cardiogenic shock at the time of admission to intensive care unit	Chronic heart failure
Presence of an anterior MI (left ventricular)	MI relapse
Presence of a right ventricular MI	Post-infarction angina
ECG rhythm at the time of hospital admission – sinus (with a 60-90 heart rate)	
Complete RBBB on ECG at the time of hospital admission	
White blood cell count (billions per liter)	
Time elapsed from the beginning of the CHD attack to the hospital	
Use of liquid nitrates in the ICU	

F. Measures for Performance Assessment

In this study, three classifiers - MLP, NB, and DT - are evaluated based on several metrics:

1. Accuracy, which denotes the proportion of accurate predictions out of the total.
2. Error rate, referring to the fraction of incorrect predictions within the total of predictions.
3. The Kappa statistic is a normalized measure of agreement [17]. Kappa values range between -1 and 1. It is important to note that a Kappa value of 1 represents perfect agreement, whereas a value of 0 indicates agreement not better than random chance. Furthermore, if the Kappa value is greater than 0, the classifier performs superiorly compared to random chance. A negative Kappa value signifies an agreement inferior to that expected by mere chance.
4. F-Measure: This metric amalgamates recall and precision measures into a singular performance indicator.
5. Matthew's Correlation Coefficient (MCC) is a means for calculating the difference between predicted and actual values [18].
6. The area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve is commonly used for measuring the classifier performance [19]. The ROC curve is drawn by plotting the True Positive Rate (TPR) on the y-axis and the False Positive Rate (FPR) on the x-axis. The classifier performs better when the ROC curve is closer to the upper left corner.

Although accuracy and error rate are deemed crucial and effective metrics, they possess certain limitations in the context of imbalanced data. Consequently, alternative measures such as Kappa statistic (k), F-measure, and MCC offer more insightful evaluations as they account for class balance and diverse error types. Given the MI complications, the derived data are imbalanced. These alternative metrics were proven to be essential for this research.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results of MLP, NB, and DT for All Attributes

Figure 1 presents the accuracy and error rate results. The accuracy metrics obtained by the MLP, NB, and DT classifiers were 90%, 79%, and 88%, correspondingly. The MLP classifier consistently delivered superior performance.

Fig. 1. Accuracy and error rate for MLP, NB, and DT.

Table II displays the Kappa statistic results obtained for the three classifiers. The values for these classifiers were 0.6292, 0.4036, and 0.4654. Upon evaluating these outcomes, it can be inferred that the 3 classifiers employed in our model exhibited effective performance as their Kappa statistics demonstrated values exceeding 0.

TABLE II. KAPPA STATISTIC VALUES

MLP	NB	DT
0.6292	0.4036	0.4654

Nevertheless, the recall percentage for NB was observed to be adversely affected. It is crucial to highlight that any variations in the level of recall measurement inhibit linear alterations in precision measurement. This phenomenon can perhaps be attributed to the substitution of False Positives (FP) and False Negatives (FN), within the denominator of the precision metric. It is well-established that higher precision and F-measure values are preferable. Consequently, as depicted in Table III, the highest F-measure value corresponded to MLP, signifying its effectiveness as a classification instrument. Furthermore, the findings revealed that the MCCs corresponding to MLP, NB, and DT were all positive, indicating satisfactory predictions by every classifier. Among them, MLP held a comparative advantage due to its superior correlation coefficient. Succinctly put, since a positive association between actual and predicted classifications prevailed in all instances, there was a high likelihood that most predicted values aligned with their true counterparts.

TABLE III. DETAILED ACCURACY BY CLASS

TP rate	FP rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC
MLP					
0.901	0.259	0.883	0.901	0.892	0.682
NB					
0.791	0.227	0.861	0.791	0.822	0.493
DT					
0.881	0.513	0.832	0.881	0.851	0.489

As illustrated in Table III, the specific accuracy of every class-classification employing MLP, NB, and DT classifiers is presented. The results demonstrated that the recall and precision percentages of all the classifiers were relatively close to one another as their values did not exhibit a significant disparity. Figure 2 represents the ROC curves for the three classifiers. It can be observed that the MLP classifier demonstrates the best performance, as its ROC curve is closer to the top-left corner, followed closely by DT.

Fig. 2. Roc curves for MLP, NB, and DT algorithms for all attributes.

A. Results after using the WEKA Attribute Selection Technique

Figure 3 displays the accuracy and error rates for MLP, NB, and DT when reducing the dataset through the use of the attribute selection technique. The DT classifier exhibited a higher accuracy percentage, signifying its effectiveness as a classification instrument. Interestingly, the accuracy percentages of MLP and NB were quite comparable. Consequently, the DT classifier demonstrated lower error rate as opposed to those achieved by MLP and NB. It is noteworthy that MLP lower accuracy percentage was not observed when analyzing the full dataset.

Fig. 3. Accuracy and error rate for MLP, NB, and DT.

The results of the Kappa statistics, as determined by the three classifiers, are exhibited in Table IV. All values for this metric were positive, denoting that the classifiers displayed efficient performance within the analytical model. In regard to the full dataset, the MLP classifier yielded the highest Kappa statistic. However, when employing the attribute selection method, this value became the lowest.

TABLE IV. KAPPA STATISTIC VALUES

MLP	NB	DT
0.4717	0.4843	0.4875

Table V illustrates the comprehensive accuracy of each class-classification technique, using the MLP, NB, and DT classifiers. Based on these findings, it is evident that the MLP and NB classifiers produced nearly identical percentage results. Both MLP and NB demonstrated high levels of precision and recall with a preference for the DT classifier. Specifically, the most elevated percentages were attributed to the DT classifier. Regarding the F-measure criterion, all classifiers displayed effective performance as their F-measure percentages were consistently higher in every instance. Among the classifiers employed in this research, the DR classifier was deemed more favorable. In relation to the MCC measure, all the algorithms exhibited positive correlation coefficients. Notably, DT's MCC surpassed those achieved by MLP and NB.

TABLE V. DETAILED ACCURACY BY CLASS FOR MLP, NB AND DT

TP rate	FP rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC
MLP					
0.864	0.400	0.834	0.864	0.849	0.510
NB					
0.861	0.378	0.845	0.861	0.853	0.512
DT					
0.894	0.540	0.968	0.894	0.921	0.547

The ROC curves obtained by the three classifiers are displayed in Figure 4. The DT classifier introduced the best performance, as its ROC curve was closer to the upper left corner. Yet, the performance of the MLP and NB classifiers did not differ significantly.

Fig. 4. ROC curves for MLP, NB and DT algorithms after using the WEKA attribute selection technique.

Upon evaluating all three classifiers concurrently, the MLP classifier showed optimal performance for the full MI complications dataset. This finding is well documented in previous studies [3]. In contrast, the DT classifier emerged as a more favorable classifier when the dataset sample size was diminished through the attribute selection algorithm, followed by NB. The DT and NB findings are in line with the findings in [2, 3], according to which both classifiers are appropriate under a small number of attributes.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study has examined the myocardial infarction complications that could potentially lead to lethal consequences. The primary objective of this article was to evaluate the effectiveness of MPL, NB, and DT classifiers in categorizing myocardial infarction complications and predicting lethal outcomes. A comparison between classifiers was made, either employing an attribute selection algorithm or not. The findings provided an overall perspective on the efficacy of various machine learning models in distinguishing myocardial infarction complications and predicting mortality resulting from these complications. It was evident from the results that classifier performance may fluctuate based on multiple factors such as data sample size and their features. Therefore, these aspects must be considered when deciding which classifiers are most suitable for handling data concerning myocardial infarction complications.

In the context of analyzing myocardial infarction complications, and using the full dataset (large sample size), it was observed that the MPL had a superior performance over the NB and DT classifiers, with DT being a close second. Among the classification algorithms employed in this research, MPL emerged as the most effective, achieving an accuracy rate of up to 90%. NB exhibited the lowest accuracy rate, translating to moderate performance in classifying myocardial infarction complications. While NB may still be applicable to the myocardial infarction data utilized in this study, it is crucial to acknowledge that this classifier might be a less favorable option for predicting lethal outcomes when compared to more sophisticated classifiers like MPL for large data samples.

Upon employing the WEKA attribute selection algorithm, DT was consistently proved to be the most superior classifier in terms of accuracy, demonstrating the highest accuracy rate with a smaller sample size. This suggests that the implementation of attribute selection algorithms augmented DT accuracy and subsequently heightened its ability to categorize myocardial infarction complication cases. Furthermore, it can be discerned that DT performance experienced significant improvement as the sample size diminished. Additionally, it is important to note that MLP values were lower than those derived from other classifiers. This signifies that when data instances (sample size) decrease, the classification correctness rate dependent on MPL also decreases. Hence, MLP performance was more effective on large datasets.

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Human Activity Recognition through Smartphone Inertial Sensors with ML Approach

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ABSTRACT

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) has several applications in healthcare, security, and assisted living systems used in smart homes. The main aim of these applications or systems is to classify body movement read from the built in sensors such as accelerometers and gyroscopes. Some actions could be performed in response to the output of these HAR systems. The number of smartphone users increases, whereas the sensors are widely available in different sizes and shapes (internal or external sensors). Recent advances in sensor technology and machine learning have led researchers to conduct studies on sensor technology such as HAR. HAR systems typically use a combination of sensors, such as accelerometers, gyroscopes, and cameras, to collect images or signal data that can be classified by machine learning algorithms. HAR research has focused on several key challenges including dealing with variability in sensor data, handling missing data or noise, and dealing with large amounts of sensor-generated data. In this work, several machine learning algorithms were tested in predefined settings using the KU-HAR dataset in a series of experiments. Subsequently, various performance metrics were calculated to assess the chosen algorithms' performance. The experimental findings showed that the LightGBM classifier surpassed the other machine learning algorithms in performance metrics, such as accuracy, F1 score, precision, and recall. Although Gradient Boosting has lengthy training time, the other classifiers complete their training in an acceptable time period.

Keywords-Human Activity Recognition (HAR); accelerometer; gyroscope; machine learning; sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

The domain of Human Activity Recognition (HAR) is rapidly expanding, leveraging sensor data to autonomously detect and categorize human behaviors and actions, in numerous applications. The field of wearable computing is also experiencing rapid growth in activity recognition, thanks to sensors embedded in smartphones. Advances in smartphone technology have enabled these built-in sensors to collect time-series data in real-time, paving the way for a variety of applications in health monitoring, sports, gaming, and security. Table I shows that the number of smartphone users in the USA was 307 million in 2022 and is expected to reach 311.8 million in 2023. Every year, there are 4 million new users added to these statistics [1]. Thus, HAR applications will aid smartphone users in terms of health monitoring, sports performance, etc. Human activity tracking based on computer vision has been

widely used, but infrastructure support is required to implement such systems, e.g. mounting some cameras in the monitoring areas [2]. Alternatively, inertial sensors available in smartphones—such as accelerometers and gyroscopes—can be worn on the body to measure acceleration and orientation [3]. An inertial sensor is a device that measures acceleration, angular velocity, and, sometimes, magnetic fields. The term encompasses a range of sensors, including accelerometers and gyroscopes [4]. A triaxial sensor specifically refers to a type of inertial sensor that measures these parameters along three orthogonal axes [5]. In essence, all triaxial sensors are inertial sensors, but not all inertial sensors are necessarily triaxial. Some may measure only one or two parameters and may not be oriented along three axes.

HAR based on smartphones is a supervised classification problem in which subjects perform activities to obtain a training dataset [6]. This approach involves collecting sensor

data from smartphones worn by individuals during their daily routines. Using supervised learning techniques, the data acquired from smartphones are used to train algorithms that can accurately categorize and recognize different activities performed by users. The success of HAR lies in its ability to bridge the gap between raw sensor information and meaningful insights into human behaviors and movements.

TABLE I. SMARTPHONE USERS IN THE USA [3]

Year	Smartphone users (millions)
2022	307
2023	311.80
2024	316.20
2025	320.40
2026	324.40
2027	328.20
2028	331.80
2029	335.20
2030	338.50
2031	341.70
2032	344.70
2033	347.60

This study makes use of KU-HAR, a publicly available real-world HAR dataset [7], which contains 18 activities collected from 90 individuals. Our research focuses on refining the performance of activity recognition models through feature extraction and ML methods. Through this process, we aim to achieve optimal results, thereby enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of our classification algorithms. This approach advances our understanding of activity recognition and significantly contributes to the development of robust and precise models for real-world applications. In conclusion, our goals have been met through the presentation of results obtained by employing 7 Machine Learning (ML) classifiers: Gradient Boosting (GB), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), XGBoost, LightGBM, and Catboost. The contributions of this study are summarized as follows:

- First, we explore various relevant research areas for collecting HAR datasets and utilizing different machines as well as deep learning classifiers.
- We analyze the KU-HAR dataset, which includes a variety of dynamic and static activities and a large scale of samples. Additionally, we utilize ML algorithms to assess the classification performance of the HAR system.
- Lastly, we conduct a comprehensive evaluation of our system across various performance metrics such as precision, accuracy, recall, and F1-score. We also calculate the training and prediction durations to provide a thorough understanding of the system's operational efficiency.

II. RELATED WORK

HAR applications are utilized across various research fields. Researchers present HAR applications differently due to the variability in the modality of human activity data [7]. One such dataset was published in [8] (University of California, Irvine (UCI)- ML Repository). This dataset consists of 30 subjects performing 6 activities: standing, sitting, laying,

walking downstairs, walking upstairs, and walking. A total of 10,299 samples were collected, each with 561 features in time-series format, using built-in smartphone sensors. This dataset has been widely used by researchers and has achieved high levels of accuracy. In 2013, a proposed system achieved an overall accuracy of 96% on the UCI dataset [9]. The Wireless Sensor Data Mining (WISDM) dataset [10] has become a benchmark in the field of HAR. The dataset consists of 5,424 transformed samples collected from 29 participants who performed 6 activities [10]. The authors trained models using robust algorithms such as J48, Logistic Regression (LR), and Multilayer Perceptron, achieving accuracies of 85.1%, 78.1%, and 91.7%, respectively. In [11], the authors applied the ADABOOST.M1 algorithm using 6 different classifiers: Hoeffding Tree, Decision Stump, Random Tree, J48, RF, and REP Tree on the same dataset, achieving accuracies of 87.84%, 57.31%, 95.69%, 97.83%, 94.44%, and 97.33%, respectively. In [12], the USC-HAD dataset focusing on daily activities was collected to enhance ubiquitous computing. The researchers enlisted 14 subjects to perform 12 different activities, resulting in a total of 840 samples. This dataset includes a diverse range of activities suitable for various applications in activity recognition. In [13], various techniques were employed using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) on the previously mentioned dataset, achieving a high accuracy of 97.01%.

Fall detection systems are essential for reducing healthcare costs and are a leading cause of severe injuries among seniors. The UMAFALL dataset [14] utilizes multisensory data from different body points of each participant, which enhances the performance of automatic fall detection systems. The UMAFALL dataset consists of sample data from 17 subjects using accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer sensors. The authors employed a 200 Hz sampling rate to classify activities into 11 classes. Authors in [15] applied various methods to this dataset and achieved the highest accuracy of 98.49% using Shallow MLP. Additional notable accuracies include 97.8% with RF and 95.87% with KNN. The system in [16] relies on an accelerometer sensor module and collects HAR data using the Microsoft Band 2, positioned on the wrist. The sensors sample data at a frequency of 62 Hz. Time-series data are segmented using sliding windows with a 50% overlap. To capture a full cycle of human activity, the sliding windows are set to a size of 64, covering a time span of approximately 1 s. This experiment achieved an overall accuracy rate of approximately 90% using an RF model. Authors in [17] focused on optimizing classification algorithms for HAR systems that employ wearable devices. The paper takes an in-depth look at the utilization of RF algorithms for feature selection. According to the findings, using RF for this purpose enhances the memory efficiency of the model, particularly for mobile applications, although there is a slight compromise in accuracy. The study reports achieving a high accuracy rate of 92.7% when employing the Support Vector Classifier (SVC). Furthermore, accuracies of 89.99% and 92.79% were achieved using KNN and LR algorithms, respectively. Table II provides a comparative summary of the findings from previous research along with the results obtained from our proposed models.

TABLE II. COMPARISON OF OUR WORK WITH PREVIOUSLY PROPOSED MODELS

Ref.	Year	Dataset	Classes	Activities	ML/DL	Algorithms	Accuracy
[9]	2012	UCI-HAR	6	Standing, sitting, laying, walking_downstairs, walking_upstairs, walking	ML	SVM (MC-SVM)	96%
[10]	2012	WISDM	6	Jogging, walking, downstairs, upstairs, standing, sitting	BOTH	J48, LR, MLP	85.1%, 78.1%, 91.7%
[12]	2012	USC-HAD	12	Walking left, walking forward, walking upstairs, walking right, walking downstairs, jumping, standing, running forward, sitting, sleeping, elevator down, elevator up	DL	DCNN	97.01%
[14]	2017	UMAFALL	11	Climbing stairs down, climbing stairs up, squatting, light jogging, lying down and getting up from a bed, hopping, walking, sitting down and up from a chair, fall activities (forward, backwards, lateral)	BOTH	Shallow MLP, RF, KNN	98.49%, 97.8%, 95.87%
[16]	2017	Not Reported	6	Walking, going upstairs, going downstairs, jumping, running, keeping static	ML	RF	90%
[17]	2022	UCI-HAR	6	Standing, sitting, laying, walking_downstairs, walking_upstairs, walking	ML	KNN, LR, SVC	89.99%, 92.79%, 93.47%
Proposed	2023	KU-HAR	18	Stand, lay, sit, talk-stand, talk-sit, stair-up, lay-stand, stair-down, stand-sit, table-tennis, pick, push-up, jump, sit-up, walk-backward, walk, run, walk-circle	ML	RF, KNN, DT, XGBoosting, GB, LightGBM, CatBoost	94%, 77%, 87%, 95%, 94%, 96%, 91%

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND PRE-PROCESSING

The process of developing a HAR model using a specific dataset involves several key steps. Initially, a thorough understanding of the dataset is required, followed by the crucial task of data cleaning. Subsequently, the application of robust statistical methods is essential to ensure that the study's objectives are met and aligned with predetermined performance metrics. This section provides an overview of the approach used to analyze and pre-process the KU-HAR dataset.

A. Dataset

The KU-HAR Dataset [7] was collected by students from the Electronics and Communication Engineering Department of Khulna University. It consists of 18 different activities performed by individuals, such as stand, lay, sit, etc., and is presented in a time-series format. The dataset consists of three Comma-Separated Values (CSV) files: raw activity data, which include 1945 samples across 18 classes, trimmed and interpolated raw data, which are cleaned of natural noise occurring during the collection process, and a set of 20,750 subsamples extracted from the raw data. We intend to use these subsamples to build our proposed system. This dataset is segmented into 3 s intervals for each corresponding activity, capturing data from each axis (x, y, z) and each sensor (accelerometer and gyroscope). The data were collected from 90 subjects aged between 18 and 34 years using built-in smartphone sensors, namely accelerometers and gyroscopes. Figure 1 presents the frequency distribution of each class label. While the frequency of some class labels is moderately high, other models have comparatively lower. This variance in label distribution is what continues to make the KU-HAR dataset a subject of ongoing research interest, offering opportunities for contributions in both existing and new ML algorithms. Figure 2 represents a sample of accelerometer data for each activity to distinguish between static and dynamic activities. Static activities include standing, sitting, laying, and talk-standing, while dynamic activities encompass actions like walking, jumping, running, etc. Through sampling each activity, we

observed that static activities exhibit higher data density compared to dynamic activities, thereby posing challenges for machine classification. For this study, we utilized Python 3 to process the data and develop models. We also employed various existing packages to facilitate the classification and evaluation processes. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) was applied to understand and analyze the dataset using statistical techniques and visualizations. This enabled us to discern relationships between features and identify patterns and anomalies. EDA techniques have been employed to ensure that the dataset is clean and ready for classification [18].

Fig. 1. Class frequency.

B. Description of Activities

In HAR systems, activities are generally categorized into static and dynamic. Static activities typically involve minimal or no movement, whereas dynamic activities entail significant motion or changes in position. Table III lists the static and dynamic activities featured in the KU-HAR dataset. Static activities involve relatively little or no change in position and include actions such as standing, sitting, laying, or talking

while being stationary. Dynamic activities, on the other hand, entail significant motion or changes in position, exemplified by walking, running, jumping, or performing exercises like push-ups and sit-ups [19]. Categorizing activities as either static or dynamic is advantageous for designing and training HAR systems. This is because the features and algorithms employed for recognizing these activities may differ based on their motion characteristics.

Fig. 2. Accelerometer samples for each activity.

TABLE III. STATIC AND DYNAMIC ACTIVITES IN KU-HAR

Dynamic Activities	Static Activities
Pick	Sit
Jump	Lay
Push-up	Stand-sit
Walk-circle	Talk-stand
Walk	Stand
Walk-backwards	Talk-sit
Sit-up	
Run	
Lay-stand	
Stair-up	
Stair-down	
Table-tennis	

C. The Proposed Model

After reviewing the related work in HAR, we devised the model depicted in Figure 3. Initially, for the KU-HAR dataset, we utilized the 3 s subsamples created by [7] for each activity. We then applied a feature extraction technique to derive a new

set of time-domain features, which are detailed later (Table VI). Subsequently, we conducted data cleaning and duplicate checks to ensure the dataset is ready for training. The data were then partitioned into training and testing sets, with a distribution of 70% for training and 30% for testing. We trained our HAR model using this dataset and evaluated its performance using various metrics, which will be elaborated below.

Fig. 3. The proposed model.

D. Evaluation Metrics

We evaluated our work using a variety of metrics, namely precision, accuracy, F1-score, recall, training time, and prediction time. We acknowledge that a high-accuracy model alone does not guarantee the reliability of the classifier's predictions. To assess the consistency of our system's results, we employed additional methods, such as the confusion matrix. Table IV provides a simplified representation of a confusion matrix for a hypothetical 3-class problem, which in our case extends to an 18-class problem [20].

TABLE IV. CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual Class	Predicted Class		
	Class A	Class B	Class C
Class A	TP-A-A	FP-A-B	FP-A-C
Class B	FN-B-A	TP-B-B	FP-B-C
Class C	FN-C-A	FN-C-B	TP-C-C

TP_A_A demonstrates the true positives for Class A (have correctly predicted as Class A), FP_A_B demonstrates the false positives for Class A when predicted as Class B, FN_A_B demonstrates the false negatives for Class A when the actual class is B. The evaluation metrics can be calculated using the formulas outlined in Table V.

- Precision: This metric quantifies the proportion of accurately identified instances of each specific activity among all instances classified under that particular activity. This is evaluated across the 18 different activities.
- Accuracy: This represents the percentage of activity records correctly identified, taking into account all 18 classes.
- F1-score: This composite metric calculates the harmonic mean of recall and precision for each of the 18 classes in the HAR problem, offering a balanced measure of classification performance.
- Recall: This metric measures the proportion of correctly predicted instances for each specific activity relative to all instances of that activity. It provides a comprehensive assessment of the classifier's ability to accurately identify each of the 18 activities.

- Training time: Denotes the time required to train the model using a specific algorithm across the entire dataset.
- Prediction time: Indicates the time taken by a specific algorithm to predict activities across the entire dataset, differentiating among various types of activities.

E. Feature Extraction

From each sample mentioned above, a feature vector is derived. These features are based on standard methods commonly used in HAR studies considering smartphones [21]. For instance, metrics like mean and standard deviation were utilized [22]. A total of 66 features, spanning both frequency and time domains, were extracted to describe each activity window [23, 24]. To derive features from the data, we utilized a window-based approach rather than relying on raw data, which would require classification for each individual data point [25]. Table VI presents the extracted features along with their corresponding mathematical equations.

TABLE V. EVALUATION METRICS

Metric	Mathematical equation
Accuracy (ACC)	$\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$
Precision (Pr)	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
Recall (Rc)	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
F1-Score (F1)	$\frac{2TP}{2TP+FP+FN}$

TABLE VI. MATHEMATICAL REPRESENTATION OF THE EXTRACTED FEATURES

Feature	Equation
Mean	$\mu_s = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n S_i$
Max	$\max(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n)$
Min	$\min(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n)$
Median	$\text{median}(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n)$
Standard Deviation (SD)	$\sigma_s = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \mu_s)^2}$
Skewness	$\frac{1}{n\sigma_s^3} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \mu_s)^3$
Kurtosis	$\frac{1}{n\sigma_s^4} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \mu_s)^4$
Signal magnitude area	$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i + y_i + z_i)$
Interquartile range	percentile (s, 75) – percentile (s, 25)
Average energy	$e = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i^2$
Entropy	$H(X) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p(x_i) \log_2 p(x_i)$

F. Data Processing and ML Tool

In this experiment, we utilized the Jupyter Notebook running on Python version 3.11. Although the Anaconda platform offers various notebook applications, we chose Python for its efficiency, scalability, and robustness. Additionally, Python offers a wide array of evaluation metrics that aid in assessing the performance of the models we used. To process the data, train the models, and evaluate their performance, we employed several libraries, including Sklearn, Numpy, SciPy, Pandas, CatBoost, LightGBM, and XGBoost [26–32].

G. Data Partitioning

The dataset was divided into separate training and testing subsets in a 70:30 ratio. This separation was conducted using randomization and stratification methods to ensure that all classes were represented in both subsets. Following this division, we employed the training data to construct various classification models. Ultimately, these models were evaluated on the testing dataset to assess their performance [33, 34].

IV. MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFIERS

This section offers a concise overview of various supervised ML algorithms, highlighting their significance in diverse domains like HAR. The ongoing advancement of cutting-edge technologies underscores the growing need for these algorithms, which are crucial for extracting knowledge from large datasets. In this study, we aim to utilize these ML algorithms to classify the extracted features from the KU-HAR dataset into their corresponding classes. Introduced in 2001, the RF algorithm has gained widespread use for classification and regression tasks. This algorithm involves combining multiple DTs that are generated in a randomized manner and then aggregating their predictions through averaging. It has proven especially effective when dealing with a high number of variables compared to the number of observations [35]. RF is well-suited for HAR applications, as it is an ensemble learning algorithm that can work with various types of datasets, including time series data. One of its primary advantages in the field of HAR is its ability to manage complex, high-dimensional datasets. Moreover, RF is robust to noise and outliers, making it valuable for reliable activity recognition in real-world scenarios [36]. KNN algorithm is a form of supervised learning that classifies new data points based on their proximity to the K closest existing points. The value of K is a significant hyperparameter that dictates how many neighbors should be considered [37]. The algorithm functions by initially calculating the distance between a new data point and every other point in the training dataset. The instances with the shortest distances are then identified as the K nearest neighbors. The new instance is subsequently labeled based on the most common label among its K closest neighbors. One of the most commonly used distance metrics is the Euclidean distance:

$$d(x_i, x_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{l=1}^m (x_{il} - x_{jl})^2}$$

DT is a powerful algorithm used for classification and prediction [38]. Essentially, it is a tree-like model that serves as

a flowchart, consisting of branches, nodes, and leaves. The algorithm divides a dataset into smaller subsets while simultaneously constructing an associated DT.

LR assumes a linear relationship among the features of a dataset. This categorizes it as a parametric learning algorithm, adhering to a predefined structure for the model's parameters. While LR is typically used for predicting outcomes with continuous values, it can also be adapted for classification tasks. Given that time-series data consist of continuous values, LR could yield favorable results for classification [39]. In our case with 18 classes, the model calculates the probability of an input belonging to a specific class j , as expressed by:

$$P(y = j|\mathbf{x}) = \frac{e^{x \cdot \mathbf{w}_j + b_j}}{\sum_{k=1}^{18} e^{x \cdot \mathbf{w}_k + b_k}}$$

GB is a powerful ML technique used for both classification and regression tasks. This ensemble learning approach constructs a predictive model by sequentially combining the outputs of multiple weaker models, often DTs. The overall performance is continually enhanced by applying a loss function at each iteration and optimizing it through the Gradient Descent algorithm [40]. The general mathematical form of the Gradient Descent algorithm is given by:

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \alpha \cdot h_m(x)$$

XGBoost is a form of supervised learning in the ML domain. It uses boosting techniques to create accurate models. Essentially, it employs DTs for making predictions. The term boosting refers to the construction of a sequence of models, where each new model aims to address the shortcomings of the previous one [41].

LightGBM is a sophisticated ML technique that employs a histogram-based algorithm and a leaf-wise strategy to enhance model accuracy [42]. One of the main advantages of LightGBM is its capability for GPU acceleration, enabling the model to train and make predictions faster than some other algorithms.

CatBoost is a supervised ML algorithm tailored for classification and regression tasks. Its name is derived from Categorical Boosting. The algorithm incorporates advanced techniques to improve predictive model accuracy, making it a valuable tool in the field of ML for structured data analysis.

V. MODEL PERFORMANCE AND DISCUSSION

Table VII presents the results obtained from the various ML classifiers discussed above. After the evaluation of the performance with precision, recall, accuracy, and F1-score, the LightGBM classifier emerges as the top performer, followed by XGBoost, RF, GB, CatBoost, DT, and KNN. Notably, XGBoost, RF, and LightGBM excel in terms of higher accuracy and well-balanced precision and recall. DT, GB, and CatBoost also show commendable performance, while KNN lags slightly in accuracy and other metrics.

During the experiment, we also measured the training and prediction times, as shown in Table VIII. It's evident that KNN requires a significantly longer duration for both training and testing phases. Upon analyzing the training and prediction

times across various classifiers, we observed distinct differences in computational efficiency. While KNN is notable for its relatively quick training time, it demands considerably more time for making predictions. In contrast, RF has a lengthier training phase but excels in prediction, delivering quick results once trained. The DT classifier offers a balanced approach with both short training and prediction times, making it an overall efficient choice. Ensemble methods such as GB, XGBoost, LightGBM, and CatBoost require longer training durations due to their intricate ensembles but make up for it with efficient prediction times. This highlights the trade-offs between training and prediction speeds.

TABLE VII. CLASSIFIERS' PERFORMANCE

Classifier	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
KNN	0.94008	0.940068	0.940751	0.94008
RF	0.771084	0.767235	0.771158	0.771084
DT	0.867149	0.867198	0.867774	0.867149
GB	0.94008	0.939989	0.940512	0.94008
XGBoosting	0.952129	0.952057	0.95238	0.952129
LightGBM	0.958072	0.957996	0.958361	0.958072
CatBoost	0.911004	0.910832	0.911173	0.911004

TABLE VIII. TRAINING AND PREDICTION TIMES

Classifier	Training Time (s)	Prediction Time (s)
KNN	0.005913	1.533868
RF	12.077085	0.121668
DT	1.793583	0.003753
GB	584.24576	0.145591
XGBoosting	50.149573	0.07401
LightGBM	10.617264	0.196468
CatBoost	21.677018	0.013404

After feature extraction, which yielded a total of 66 features, we compared the performance of this reduced dataset to the original segmented dataset. We evaluated the various ML classifiers on both datasets and the results are presented in Table IX. The findings indicate that the 66-feature dataset generally outperforms the 1800-feature dataset across all assessed metrics. Not only is the performance higher, but it is also more consistent for classifiers using the 66 features, as evidenced by lower variability. Figure 6 illustrates the difference in accuracy between each model using both the original and the extracted datasets.

Fig. 6. Model accuracy comparison.

Table X offers a brief analysis of the results derived from the confusion matrix. Firstly, the misclassified labels encompass both FP and FN across all classes. Secondly, the

error rate is determined as the ratio of the total number of misclassified samples to the overall count of samples in the confusion matrix. Our findings indicate that LightGBM has the lowest error rate (0.042), thereby making it the most accurate classifier based on this particular metric. Conversely, KNN has the highest error rate (0.228).

We also noted that LightGBM has the highest number of true positives (5964), signifying it correctly classified more instances compared to other classifiers. In contrast, KNN has the lowest number of true positives (4800).

TABLE IX. PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR ORIGINAL AND EXTRACTED DATASET

Classifier	#Features	Accuracy	F1 Score	Precision	Recall
RF	1800	0.783614	0.767101	0.803174	0.783614
RF	66	0.94008	0.940068	0.940751	0.94008
KNN	1800	0.429558	0.401098	0.506774	0.429558
KNN	66	0.771084	0.767235	0.771158	0.771084
DT	1800	0.470843	0.468254	0.467726	0.470843
DT	66	0.867149	0.867198	0.867774	0.867149
GB	1800	0.827952	0.824933	0.830015	0.827952
GB	66	0.94008	0.939989	0.940512	0.94008
XGBoosting	1800	0.865221	0.865221	0.862785	0.865221
XGBoosting	66	0.952129	0.952057	0.95238	0.952129
LightGBM	1800	0.869558	0.865922	0.873129	0.869558
LightGBM	66	0.958072	0.957996	0.958361	0.958072
CatBoost	1800	0.789237	0.785696	0.790512	0.789237
CatBoost	66	0.911004	0.910832	0.911173	0.911004

TABLE X. CONFUSION MATRIX ANALYSIS

Classifier	TP	Total elements	Misclassified	Error rate
Catboost	5671	6225	554	0.089
DT	5354	6225	871	0.14
RF	5845	6225	380	0.061
XGBoost	5550	5848	298	0.051
Light GBM	5964	6223	259	0.042
KNN	4800	6219	1419	0.228
GB	5487	5850	363	0.062

The results of this study can be summarized as follows:

- Based on all four evaluation metrics, the LightGBM classifier emerged as the best model among the ones considered.
- Despite having high training and prediction times, GB performs exceptionally well, showing results quite similar to those of LightGBM.
- XGBoost ranks second in performance, with a training time of 50 s, compared to LightGBM's 10 s.
- RF and LightGBM offer a good balance between reasonable training times and high performance.
- Although DT and KNN have the shortest training times, their overall performance metrics are the lowest.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a series of experiments in Human Activity Recognition (HAR) was conducted to assess the effectiveness and consistency of seven distinct machine learning algorithms, namely Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, Decision Tree, KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM. These experiments leverage the publicly available KU-HAR dataset, which encompasses 18 activity classes grouped into static and dynamic categories. The results indicate that the LightGBM

algorithm consistently outperforms the others across many performance metrics such as accuracy, F1 score, recall, and precision. While Gradient Boosting demonstrated higher effectiveness but required an extended training period, the remaining algorithms completed their training within a reasonable timeframe.

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Applying the Analytical Hierarchy Process to Identify the Challenges and Priorities of Reconstruction Projects in Iraq

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ABSTRACT

Reconstruction project management in the cities of Mosul, Anbar, and Tikrit, in Iraq still faces major obstacles that impede the comprehensive performance of these projects. It is thus necessary to improve the arising challenge estimation in the implementation of reconstruction projects and evaluate their components: time, cost, quality, and scope. This study used the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) to prioritize major and minor criteria in the influential causes of challenges and formulate a mathematical model to help decision-makers estimate them. Using the Super Decisions software, the final results indicated that changes in scope reached 40.8%, which is the greatest difficulty, followed by changes in cost at 27.6%, changes in time at 13.5%, and changes in quality at 18.11%. The results of the essential subcriteria also indicated that underlying issues still exist in the Iraqi construction industry and that quick solutions are vital. Five mathematical equations were formulated to develop a model to estimate changes that introduce challenges in time, cost, quality, and scope and so to help decision-makers assess the level of these changes and identify challenges. This study recommended addressing these variables through realistic administrative and methodological strategies to consider changes, challenges, and available opportunities.

Keywords-challenges; AHP; reconstruction; cost overrun; time overrun

I. INTRODUCTION

Reconstruction is known as the process of returning building facilities to their natural state after war, planning errors, destruction for political motives, or after a natural disaster. Through this procedure, the damaged buildings are replaced or developed in a way that serves the country's economic growth. Reconstruction is an integrated concept that includes moving to a position of stability and peace. Reconstruction areas are divided into two main sections: physical and non-physical [1]. Reconstruction is associated with the architectural concepts of restoration (repairing existing building fabric) and preservation (preventing further decay), where the most comprehensive form is to create a destroyed building replica. Reconstruction is the act or process of photographing, by new construction, the form, features, and details of a non-existent site, landscape, building, structure, or object to replicate its appearance in a specific period and historic location [2]. It involves a process using the same materials and methods as closely as possible to the original ones or existing original components, particularly in buildings

of cultural and historical importance, which then serve as objects of display and museums. However, in many cases, the rebuilding of a building to its original and typical form may not meet the requirements due to a lack of resources, such as a facade plans or document photos [1].

Reconstruction projects go through four stages, starting with monitoring the current situation and estimating losses. Then, executive plans and programs are developed, including identifying implementation mechanisms, participating parties, means of financing, and other details. Later, the implementation stage and project operation take place, followed by the maintenance stage and evaluation after operations. The first stage is considered the most important and dangerous, as shortcomings can ruin the whole process and threaten the whole project with failure [3]. The reconstruction process not only needs to assess economic needs by dealing with affected individuals or the facts on the ground but also needs to study political and social dimensions, which are crucial and are often overlooked. Before economies can be rebuilt or political institutions can be revitalized, societies must deal with these challenges [4]. There is no doubt that economic

factors affect the results associated with reconstruction, which is evident in the three basic conditions that must be met for the process to be successful [5]:

- The availability of economic resources for reconstruction
- The presence or absence of a political process at national or regional level
- Economic structures, institutional legacy, and state relations.

Successful reconstruction is based on effective state-building as well as sustainable, balanced, and long-term economic recovery. If these factors are incomplete or missing, reconstruction can be disrupted, giving external actors greater scope to influence the course of this process to serve their agendas. Despite the availability of financial allocations and grants for the reconstruction of liberated cities, the Iraqi government needs help to fulfill its obligations and promises to complete the demolished homes, schools, hospitals, and infrastructure. However, it faces many different pressures and challenges that affect weak implementation, as represented in most local studies and scientific discussions, including the following [6]:

- External factors outside the institution's ability to influence, represented by the impact of security conditions, restrictions on oversight institution controls, the absence of necessary infrastructure to perform works, the delay in approving public budgets, inflexible laws and procedures, and the weakness of the rule of law due to the exceptional circumstances that the political process is going through.
- Internal factors specific to the institution producing services, represented by the weakness of implementing the requirements of good governance, such as transparency in decision-making, adopting competencies, and long-term planning. The weakness of good governance has been reflected in the lack of technical knowledge in project management (committees for opening and analyzing bids, department of the resident engineer, weak technical capabilities including laboratories and measuring devices), the absence of incentives for a sense of responsibility, and the centralization and complexity of administrative systems. These factors have led to delays and a lack of work mastery.
- Factors of weak integrated work between different institutions, represented by factors related to coordination between various state departments, including weak cooperation of state agencies on the issue of land allocation and in decisions to launch the disbursement of financial (Ministry of Planning) and government allocations (Ministry of Finance), and opening credits (Central Bank and Commercial Bank of Iraq).

Moving forward with the completion of some reconstruction projects in Iraq, the management aspect still needs to overcome the major obstacles that hinder the required performance of construction projects within the known determinants of success: time, cost, and specified quality. Extensive local studies are available to solve the most

important obstacles and challenges in rebuilding liberated cities after disasters, but Iraq still faces great challenges for various reasons. Many facilities and infrastructures were partially or completely destroyed, leading to large-scale displacement waves that affected the construction sector and the Iraqi economy and caused social and environmental changes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

An extensive literature review was conducted, which presents all delay factors in various reconstruction projects, focusing on Iraqi studies. The theoretical research also examined the applications of using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). It specifically explored its wide uses, and how to develop a creative tool to help the decision-maker make important decisions to identify challenges in reconstruction projects. Despite the clear difference in the environment and nature of reconstruction projects in Iraq, it was necessary to consult international studies. The most important factors regard the characteristics of customers, resources, economic and political conditions that Iraq suffers from, and managerial, organizational, and planning aspects. One of the main difficulties in reconstruction projects in Iraq is the weak coordination between the various competent authorities involved in the reconstruction process. In [7], an integrated information management system was presented through basic indicators (risk management, stakeholder management, and supply chain) by conducting a field study of critical success factors in reconstruction projects in Iraq.

Financial support is also an influential obstacle that causes the rationing of resources [8]. In [9], important criteria were tried to avoid delays and cost changes that occur in post-disaster reconstruction projects in Iraq, affecting the real duration and cost of the project versus the estimated time and cost. This study concluded that the most important factors are contractor failure, redesigns, continuous change orders, security, administrative corruption, and weather. In [10], it was shown that insufficient planning puts post-disaster reconstruction projects at risk. This study proposed an integrated approach to facilitate planning for procuring construction materials after a disaster. The collection of construction project sites using Differential Evolution (DE-K) models and the use of a matrix to prioritize a group of factors that affect the reliability of the route to reduce time can increase route reliability and reduce total resources.

In [11], the most important criteria in choosing a post-disaster project were quality, durability, accuracy, and customer satisfaction. This study also identified 21 sustainability criteria. According to [9], poor competition between contractors is the main challenge indicated by some local studies in Iraq. In [12], the interrelationship between different regions of expertise was investigated, showing that PDRP management is still in its initial stages. This study used descriptive exploratory research and qualitative data to determine cause-and-effect relationships and to identify factors that led to frequent scope changes, time and cost overruns, and low quality. The study concluded that stakeholder, risk, procurement, and communication management have a significant impact on project success. In [13], data on experience in post-disaster reconstruction projects were

collected by International Non-Governmental Organizations (INGOs), showing that it is necessary to resolve some complex issues and to identify significant differences between problems and challenges at the different locations of reconstruction projects. This study proposed a method for building project strategies to avoid failure. The study in [14] aimed to establish resilience factors and a guiding framework to assist in their selection and strategic application that can contribute to improving the resilience of reconstruction projects. This study identified 24 resilience factors, divided into 5 criteria groups, in an attempt to develop a new conceptual framework to guide developers and practitioners in improving resilience in post-disaster reconstruction projects. In [15], damaged city areas demonstrated the need to strengthen their rebuilding capacity, requiring more experienced and efficient workers to supervise projects. This study attempted to analyze the problems associated with post-disaster housing reconstruction projects in India and provide potential solutions, concluding that institutional procedures, reconstruction techniques, project implementation, and stakeholder management contribute to effective implementation.

In [16], it was indicated that most of the cities affected by disasters were not suitable for resettlement due to various cultural factors. This study suggested resolving specific cultural issues that would accelerate resettlement to achieve successful results. In [17], it was proposed that education and guiding users in successful implementation can contribute to the solution of project problems. This study also proposed how industry practitioners can use the results to implement projects through the Lean technique.

There are different trends in calculating the real challenges in reconstruction projects without considering how to identify and address them or how to help or guide the decision-maker to know the extent of the challenges or evaluate them depending on the type of project. Discrimination between different reconstruction projects in terms of the availability of resources or continuous changes in time, cost, quality, and scope is of great importance. AHP has received increasing attention in the construction industry as a clear method of complex analysis and helps the decision-maker make sound decisions among the selected alternatives. Different studies have used AHP in many fields to support multidecision criteria and applications, as it is one of the most used processes for assessing priorities [18]. AHP is regarded a multi-criteria programming and decision-making technique in complex environments. It helps to consider many criteria, set priorities, and choose alternatives in various projects and studies [19]. AHP has been widely used in complex scenarios when human perceptions, judgments, and consequences have long-term implications [20]. In [21], 77 research papers on AHP applications were reviewed, showing that risk management and sustainable construction were the most common areas of AHP application in construction management. In [22], AHP helped stakeholders identify contractors using multiple criteria without relying on the lowest price. In [23], AHP was applied to evaluate the weight of risk factors, to develop risk model assessment in construction projects, and support decision-making. Based on the coupling of the evaluation index grading criteria, in [24], a comprehensive evaluation method was developed for roof

stability grades by proposing a band-improved AHP weight assignment. In [25], AHP was used for the preliminary estimation of construction costs based on the minimum details of the project.

Previous studies that used AHP did not seek to derive mathematical relationships to facilitate the decision-maker. This study aims to facilitate decision-making in reconstruction projects, especially in the planning stage, to reach a final decision, identify challenges for projects, and evaluate them for different projects, especially since most decision-makers do not have sufficient information on how to use this analytical method or how to sort the final priorities. This study used data and results from [26] and AHP to develop mathematical equations to help the decision-maker determine the extent of the impact of the various types of challenges facing reconstruction projects in Iraq.

III. RESEARCH PROBLEMS AND OBJECTIVES

The main research problem is the continuing delays in rebuilding the liberated cities of Mosul, Anbar, and Tikrit. This issue results from the government's difficulty to make the necessary administrative arrangements to deal with these delays due to the conditions the construction environment is suffering from in Iraq. The most important ones were identified in [26]. These changes were within the determinants of cost, time, quality, and scope of work, without managing to know their proportions and determine the proportions of potential challenges. This study attempts to create a mathematical model with the help of AHP, which helps the decision-maker identify the proportions of challenges in various reconstruction projects and take advantage of the appropriate opportunity to address them. The main objective is to clarify the various changes in reconstruction projects and prepare a mathematical model that estimates the changes using several criteria. The final mathematical equations can help the decision-maker determine approximate changes in cost, time, quality, and scope of the project to initially prepare the required treatments, classify the projects based on the type of different changes, and determine the possibility of overcoming them. In addition, the developed models can help the Iraqi government prioritize the administrative challenges in reconstructing the liberated governorates.

IV. METHODOLOGY

After reviewing international and local literature on reconstruction projects and AHP applications, the high final factors leading to the fundamental challenges and opportunities in reconstruction projects in Iraq were used [26]. The former were based on the analysis of the interrelationship among different areas of expertise through cause-and-effect relationships that led to frequent changes in scope, time overruns, cost overruns, and low quality. AHP was used to determine the change priorities applying the Super Decisions software. Finally, mathematical equations were formulated.

A. Main Constraints and Related Factors

This study derived its data and aimed factors from [26], which highlighted the most important delay causes with the participation of the parties involved in the construction process

and considered their impact on the scope, cost, time, and project quality. Iraq has all the entities, resources, and professional and scientific capacity required to implement reconstruction projects. However, the decision-maker can overcome them through a scientific decision based on research studies that support his decision. Figure 2 from [26] shows the main constraints and factors related to the changes and declares the hierarchy between them, while Table I represents the relative importance factors (RII) for the final results [26].

TABLE I. RELATIVE IMPORTANCE FACTORS (RII) [26]

No.	Scope Changes	Mean	RII%
1	Diversity and number of stakeholders	4.71	94
2	Lack of communication among projects	4.61	92
3	Difficulty in building consensus	4.30	86
4	Difficulty in identifying the needs of the affected population	4.02	80
No.	Cost Overrun	Mean	RII%
1	Unrealistic financial and cost estimate	4.74	95
2	Instability of local currency exchange rate	4.24	85
3	Political instability in the country	4.12	82
4	Difficulty in developing a cost plan	3.94	79
No.	Time Overrun	Mean	RII%
1	Unrealistic schedule	4.60	92
2	Legal and bureaucratic restrictions for tendering, acquisition, and construction	4.55	91
3	Difficulty in controlling activity duration	4.44	89
4	The urgency to meet essential needs	4.35	87
No.	Low Quality	Mean	RII%
1	Dependency on imported building materials and migrant/day labor/staffing from other countries	4.55	91
2	Dependency on local sellers	4.35	87
3	The relatively large size of the damaged area	3.82	76
4	Difficulty in controlling quality	3.63	73

B. Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)

AHP suggests that a problem can be hierarchically analyzed according to the required criteria so that it is easy to examine and compare the latter independently [26]. It allows the decision maker to evaluate the alternatives systematically and scientifically through pairwise comparisons for each of the selected criteria [27]. In general, the most important steps are:

- Define the problem, the criteria affecting it, and its suggested alternatives
- Make a binary comparison between the main criteria and the subcriteria by finding their weight relative to the goal
- Gather expert opinions by determining the relative importance, and choose the geometric mean for each comparison between two criteria
- Check the consistency ratio, which should be at most 10%
- Arrange the criteria using their weights

The following stages must be followed to complete the AHP [28].

1) Building the AHP Structure

In this stage, the objective and priorities are identified and an appropriate decision model is developed with concepts and terminology discussed and analyzed using AHP. The AHP

model will decide which criteria will be used based on the statistical results. The main model consists of 3 levels (goal, clusters, nodes [29]), and the AHP structure consists of 4 clusters: scope change, time overrun, cost overrun, and low quality. Consequently, it sets up 4 nodes for all clusters, which contain the most important secondary criteria that obtained the most crucial index. These criteria are considered the most significant challenges faced and, in turn, are in line with the basic methodology objective [30], as shown in Figure 1.

2) Pairwise Comparison Matrix

After establishing the hierarchy, it is important to define the pairwise comparison, specify the comparison matrix, determine the priority vector (eigenvector), and analyze discrepancies. Criteria are evaluated in pairs to determine the relative weights between the subcriteria and the general goal. Evaluation begins with choosing the relative weight for all criteria sets [31]. Super Decisions software was used to obtain the priorities derived from the paired comparison matrices. The software calculates the eigenvector of priorities (the influence of each element on other elements) and the Consistency Ratio (CR) [32]. The Super Decisions software is structured as follows:

- It forms a hierarchical structure by analyzing the problem into clusters and nodes representing the axes and factors, respectively, as shown in Figure 1.
- After pairwise comparisons, the geometric mean of all answers is determined and entered into the program.
- The program creates the matrix, calculates the eigenvector of the priorities, and verifies the proportion of the consistency required for the success of the pairwise comparison, meaning that there is no contradiction in experts' opinions. The CR in all the pairwise comparison matrices was less than 0.1, which shows a reasonable constancy in the assessment matrix [33].

TABLE II. FUNDAMENTAL SCALE [27]

Intensity of importance	Definition
1	Equal importance
3	Moderate importance
5	Strong importance
7	Very strong importance
9	Extreme importance
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values

After completing these procedures, the following results are obtained:

- Pairwise comparisons between the four main axes and the main objective, as shown in Figure 2.
- Pairwise comparisons between the factors in these axes with the goal, as shown in Figures 3-6.
- Multiple criteria matrix, where the priorities that show the relationship between the factors were evaluated, calculated, and analyzed to determine their relative importance to the goal, as shown in Figure 7.
- Secondary criteria matrix, where the priorities show the relationship between the criteria for each factor separately.

These priorities were evaluated, calculated, and analyzed to determine their relative importance to the goal, as shown in Figure 8 for the first axis as a general model.

The responses of 23 experts, determined on a scale of 1 to 9 as shown in Table II to allow the measurement of the strength of the judgments [25], were examined.

- The 4 main axes were the final priorities of all the criteria.

Fig. 1. Snapshot of the AHP model (main window).

Fig. 2. Pairwise comparisons between the four main axes and resulting priorities.

Fig. 3. Pairwise comparisons between the factors of change in scope and resulting priorities.

Fig. 4. Pairwise comparisons between the factors of cost overrun and resulting priorities.

Fig. 5. Pairwise comparisons between the factors of time overrun and resulting priorities.

Fig. 6. Pairwise comparisons between the factors of low quality and resulting priorities.

Fig. 7. Multiple criteria matrix.

Fig. 8. Secondary criteria matrix.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table III shows the results obtained. When comparing the results for the priorities of management challenges faced by the Iraqi government for the post-disaster reconstruction of the liberated provinces, they depend first on the project's scope changes with an importance of 40.86%. This was followed by the cost overrun factor at 27.60% and the low quality of the project was 18.11%. Finally, the time-overrun factor remained the last in impact, as its importance was 13.45%. The difficulty in building consensus was the main reason that affected the scope changes at 34.7%, followed by diversity and several stakeholders at 33%, lack of communication between projects at 18.3%, and finally the difficulty in identifying the needs of the affected population at 14%.

The results for the cost overrun priorities depend first on the political instability in the country at 56.2%, and then on unrealistic financial and cost estimate reasons at 29%. The instability of the local currency exchange rate was 9.2%, and the difficulty in developing a cost plan reason remained the last at 4.7%. Importing building materials and using migrant

workers from other countries without improving the skills of local workers is the main reason for the low quality at 58.9%, followed by the difficulty in controlling quality at 22.9%, the dependence on local sellers at 13%, and the relatively large size of the damaged area at 5.2%. Time overruns were the last major challenge affecting the management of post-disaster reconstruction of Iraqi provinces. This depends mainly on the unrealistic schedule (40%), followed by the difficulty of controlling activity duration (20.6%). However, the legal and bureaucratic restrictions for tendering, acquisition, and construction reached 16.7%. Finally, the urgency to meet essential needs has the least impact at 15.7%.

The AHP results were used to formulate mathematical equations that can help stakeholders or decision-makers make decisions about the value of different variables in the project. Equations (1-5) were presented to some experts who had previously been elected to conduct AHP. The experts showed how easy it is to use these equations, applied them to some projects, and confirmed their credibility.

TABLE III. RANKING OF THE MODEL ELEMENTS

Cluster	Normalized by Cluster	Nodes	Normalized by Nodes	Limiting
Scope	0.408458	S1= Diversity and number of stakeholders	0.32987	0.118048
		S2= lack of communication among projects	0.18294	0.066234
		S3= Difficulty to build consensus	0.34737	0.342449
		S4= Difficulty in identifying the needs of the affected population	0.13983	0.035859
Cost	0.275898	C1= Unrealistic financial and cost estimate	0.29904	0.024636
		C2= Instability of local currency exchange rate	0.09206	0.009942
		C3= Political instability in the country	0.56216	0.056837
		C4= Difficulty in developing a cost plan	0.04674	0.013616
Time	0.134516	T1= Unrealistic schedule	0.47011	0.131564
		T2= Legal and bureaucratic restriction for tendering, acquisition, and construction	0.16697	0.058752
		T3= Difficulty to control activity duration	0.20625	0.019725
		T4= Urgency to meet essential needs	0.15668	0.039829
Quality	0.181129	Q1= Dependency on imported building material and migrant/day labor/staffing from other countries	0.58853	0.042536
		Q2= Dependency on local sellers	0.13038	0.021171
		Q3= Relatively large size of the damaged area	0.05219	0.011863
		Q4= Difficulty to control quality	0.2289	0.00694

VI. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

After obtaining the priorities for the main constraints and their subfactors, they were arranged in a mathematical function to facilitate the decision-makers' ability to obtain the percentage of change occurring in the four variables for any project. The mathematical relationship was formed based on the results shown in Table III as follows:

$$SC = 0.3299S1 + 0.1829S2 + 0.3474 S3 + 0.1398 S4 \tag{1}$$

where *SC* is the scope change, *S1* is the diversity and number of stakeholders, *S2* is the lack of communication between projects, *S3* is the difficulty in building consensus, and *S4* is the difficulty in identifying the needs.

$$CC = 0.299 C1 + 0.0921 C2 + 0.5622 C3 + 0.0467 C4 \tag{2}$$

where *C1* is the unrealistic financial and cost estimate, *C2* is the instability of the local currency exchange rate, *C3* is the political instability in the country, and *C4* is the difficulty in developing a cost plan.

$$TC = 0.4701 T1 + 0.1670 T2 + 0.2063T3 + 0.1567 T4 \tag{3}$$

where *TC* is the time change, *T1* is the unrealistic schedule, *T2* is the legal and bureaucratic restrictions, *T3* is the difficulty in controlling activity duration, and *T4* is the urgency to meet essential needs.

$$QC = 0.5885 Q1 + 0.1304 Q2 + 0.0522 Q3 + 0.2289 Q4 \tag{4}$$

where *QC* is the quality change, *Q1* is the dependency on imported building materials and migrant/day labor/staffing from other countries, *Q2* is the dependency on local sellers, *Q3* is the large size of the damaged area, and *Q4* is the difficulty in controlling quality. Finally,

$$RC = 0.4085SC + 0.2759CC + 0.1345TC + 0.1811QC \tag{5}$$

The total challenges of the reconstruction project are calculated through (5) after calculating the values of the four changes (time, cost, quality, and scope) to arrive at an approximate value of the number of challenges of the reconstruction project. Mathematical equations make it easier for the stakeholder or decision-maker to decide the value of different variables in the project. Equations (1-5) were presented to some experts who had previously been elected to carry out the AHP. The experts showed the ease of using these equations, which were initially applied to some projects and confirmed the credibility of the results. The final value can help the decision maker evaluate the challenges of different reconstruction projects. It can also help to compare various projects and choose the appropriate one that achieves the least challenges required to work on it within the specified strategies.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Using AHP and deducing the main changes in assessing the challenges, the decision maker can make a decisive decision on the change types of and potential challenges in reconstruction projects. They and can additionally choose the appropriate project within the available resources under the current strategic policy. This study illustrates more accurate results than previous studies because the reconstruction projects in Iraq did not rely on scientific methods to evaluate the proportion of challenges or the ability to make a qualitative comparison to choose the appropriate project within the available resources under the current strategic policy. The results showed that the priority of the changes witnessed by reconstruction projects in Iraq are the challenges of changes in the scope of the project. These challenges play a decisive role in reconstruction projects, followed by changes in cost due to poor realistic financial estimates and the reasons for the instability of the local currency exchange rate. This occurs owing to political and perhaps economic reasons emerging from the conflict in adopting sound economic thought that is applied globally. Regarding the scope of quality, its impact appears clear as an important challenge that must be addressed, especially after controlling imported building materials and

migrant labor from other countries without oversight, since the size of the affected areas in Iraq is very large and requires many resources. The time frame remains the last variable that has not received the necessary attention in all Iraqi projects, particularly after the difficulty in controlling project implementation durations for many reasons, perhaps the most prominent being the legal and bureaucratic restrictions, with suspicions of administrative corruption, lack of professional experience, and weak construction oversight work. This leads to many changes, causing delays in reconstruction projects.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

AHP was performed using Super Decisions software to determine the necessary priorities for all challenge factors in post-disaster projects and identify alternatives among the main constraints and project changes. Its direct impact on final decision-making plays a role in estimating the percentage of changes in cost, time, quality, and scope in reconstruction projects in Iraq due to the continuing delay in the return of displaced Iraqis. The study recommended the need to address these changes through realistic administrative and methodological strategies, to consider changes and available opportunities, like encouraging national industry, relying on and training local skills, resolving political reality, and providing services. The main recommendations include finding an appropriate method to secure companies operating in Iraq, adopting various computer programs from the design to the project monitoring, adapting cost and time analysis during all project stages, adhering to technical specifications and assessing quality. They also entail encouraging training workers to improve their skills, set clear time and cost schedules for evaluation and assessment, define the tasks and duties of the stockholders concerned with the reconstruction projects, and audit and control all various professional and managerial levels.

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Development of Surface Roughness Prediction and Monitoring System in Milling Process

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ABSTRACT

High surface quality is an important indicator for high-performance machining during the manufacturing process. The surface roughness generated in machining can be affected by cutting parameters and machining vibration. To achieve processing efficiency, monitoring surface quality within the desired range is important. This study aimed to develop a surface roughness prediction system for the milling process. The predictive model was established based on data collected from machining experiments with the response surface methodology. The surface roughness is related to independent variables, including cutting parameters and machining vibration, in terms of nonlinear functions by regression analysis and the neural network approach, respectively. To be implemented in a CNC milling machine for online application, a predictive model was introduced in the Virtual Machine Extension (VMX) intelligent software development platform. This model can acquire the cutting parameters from the controller via the Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture (OPCUA) interface as well as the vibration features from the sensory module. The system can calculate the roughness based on these data and issue alert when the predicted value exceeds the preset threshold or abnormal vibration is detected.

Keywords-artificial neural networks; cutting conditions; machining vibration; surface roughness

I. INTRODUCTION

With high demand of processing efficiency and high quality, high speed machining technology has been widely applied in the cutting process of machine components used in aerospace industry and 3C industry among others. In addition to high material remove rate, high surface quality is another important indicator in the manufacturing process for achieving high performance machining. Machining quality basically can be characterized by surface roughness. Basically, poor surface roughness will affect the tribological characteristics of the contact surfaces, wear behavior, and the fatigue strength of components [1-3]. The surface roughness generated on the

machined parts can be influenced by many factors such as geometry and material of cutter, workpiece material, cutting parameters, coolant conditions, machine conditions, etc. [4-7]. Cutting parameters such as axial depth of cut, spindle speed, and feed rate were shown to have great impacts on surface quality [8-10]. The optimization of cutting conditions is a prerequisite for producing better surface accuracy [11-14]. Therefore, monitoring the surface quality within the desired range is of great importance and worthy of investigation. For this purpose, authors in [14] proposed a two-pronged approach combining Machine Learning (ML) and Nondominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) to model and optimize surface roughness and tool flank wear. The experimental verification

showed that the absolute percentage errors of roughness and flank wear were 2.5% and 1.5%, respectively. Authors in [15] applied multivariable regression analysis to establish a prediction model of surface roughness based on the cutting parameters, tool wear and tool vibration. They found that feed rate is the main factor affecting surface accuracy, and spindle speed is the main factor affecting tool vibration in machining. Authors in [16] proposed a multi-objective optimization algorithm to minimize vibration amplitude and surface roughness. The objective functions and the second-order response surface models for surface roughness and vibration amplitude were created by performing regression analysis based on experimentally collected data. Authors in [17] also presented regression models in the form of nonlinear polynomial function and power-law functions to predict the surface roughness of milled surface, which were verified with higher prediction accuracy of about 90%. These studies show that the influence extent of cutting parameters on the surface roughness is different, which is dependent on machine spindle tool system, geometry characteristics and material of the cutter, workpiece material and selected cutting parameters in the experimental conditions. On the other hand, the high-speed cutting process is prone to induce chattering phenomena by the excitation of cutting force under inappropriate cutting parameters. Chatter vibration will adversely affect the surface quality and dimension accuracy of the workpiece, and cause noise and premature tool failure. In order to avoid chatter vibration, an appropriate cutting condition is necessary, which basically can be determined by the machining stability of the cutter. A cutting condition within a stable region can ensure machining without chatter and hence improve surface quality. In addition, critical cutting parameters with larger cutting depth can achieve maximum removal rate with high efficiency, but it may lead to poor surface quality due to excessive tool vibration or wear damage. Therefore, monitoring of the workpiece surface accuracy and tool damage are major concerns [18-21]. Authors in [18-19] applied sensing modules to measure the tool vibration and to detect possible damage of the tool. Authors in [21] developed a dynamic monitoring system of surface roughness by applying a neural network model. The roughness prediction model was established based on spindle speed, depth of cut, feed rate, and tool vibration in X and Z axes. Authors in [22] reported that workpiece surface morphology is affected by the vibration of the cutter in machining. They found that an increased cutting force with an increasing cutting depth and feed rate leads to higher vibration, and it accordingly augments surface roughness. Authors in [23-25] reported that surface roughness is greatly affected by the vibration amplitude of the machine tool and the axial cutting depth. The vibration levels are closely related to the cutting parameters and they become greater with an increase in the cutting speed and feed rate. Authors in [26] considered the influence of machining vibration on surface quality when establishing the surface prediction model. The input variables included cutting parameters, tooling condition, and tool vibration and were assessed in the turning process.

For improving machining quality, it is important and necessary to develop a reliable prediction model of the surface roughness, which can help engineers to detect the variation of

the surface quality in process and further confirm whether the workpiece really meets the accuracy requirements without off-line physically measurements. Online monitoring can help to immediately prognose the poor accuracy causes, making improvements and adjustments of cutting parameters, and enhance machining efficiency. This concept is also an important core technology for the development of intelligent manufacturing. Based on this concept, this study aims to develop an online surface quality monitoring system, attempting to predict the surface roughness variation in milling machining considering the machining vibration, which may be affected by tool wear with machining cycles. In this study, a series of machining experiments were conducted under various combinations of cutting conditions. The dataset collected from the experiments, including machining parameters and vibration features of the spindle tool and surface roughness of the machined parts, were used to establish the prediction model by multivariable linear regression analysis and artificial neural network modeling. Finally, a monitoring system, including the data sensing modules and data processing software, was constructed and implemented in the milling machine. The system can automatically detect the vibration state and predict the variation of surface roughness in process.

II. EXPERIMENTAL CONFIGURATION AND PROCESS

Figure 1 shows the machining experiments conducted on a vertical milling machine, in which a tungsten carbide end cutter with a diameter of 10 mm and 60 mm overhang was installed in spindle with the BT tool holder. The workpieces are Al6061 aluminum alloy blocks with dimension of $150 \times 150 \times 80$ mm. The machining process was carried out by full slot milling on the workpieces along the X-direction under different cutting parameters. In order to establish a surface roughness predictive model, valid for low speed rough machining and high speed finish machining, the cutting parameters, such as cutting depth, spindle speed, and feed rate were defined in a wide range with several levels as presented in Table I. The axial cutting depth (Z) was 1, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5 and 4.0 mm. It was defined in the stable region based on the machining stability lobe diagram of the cutter. There are 168 machining conditions defined by the different levels of cutting parameters, including 8 spindle speeds, 3 feed rates, and 7 cutting depths.

Fig. 1. Machining test and workpiece.

TABLE I. CUTTING PARAMETERS AND THEIR LEVELS

Parameters	Symbol	Levels
Spindle speed (rpm)	S	3000, 4000, 5000, 6000 7000, 8000, 9000, 10000
Cutting depth (mm)	Z	1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 3.5, 4.0
Feed rate (mm/flute)	F	0.05, 0.075, 0.10

To assess the vibration of the spindle tool in machining, accelerometers (Wilcoxon, Model 787, 500 mV/g, 22kHz) were mounted on the spindle housing to measure the vibration signals in X, Y, and Z directions simultaneously. For each slot machining, the Root Mean Square (RMS) value of the vibration signals during the milling period was calculated for further data analysis. For each machined slot, the surface roughness value (Ra) was measured at 5 equally spaced points along the feeding direction with a white light interferometer (Zygo, NewView™ 8000 Series). The mean value of the 5 measurements was calculated and collected along with the cutting parameters for subsequent analysis. The morphologies of machined surfaces and the vibration spectrum of the milling tool under specific machining conditions are illustrated in Figure 2. For example, for machining at cutting depth of 1.0 mm and speed of 4000 rpm, the surface roughness was measured as 0.834 μm . When cutting depth was increased to 2.0 mm at 7000 rpm, the roughness Ra was 2.227 μm .

Fig. 2. Surface morphologies and vibration spectrum.

III. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

A. Regression Analysis

Basically, the roughness generated on the machined surface is mainly determined by the cutting parameters and can be affected by tool vibrations induced during the machining process. The dependence of surface roughness on the process parameters can be mathematically formulated in different functions through multivariable regression analysis. Based on previous studies [17, 27], the surface roughness (Ra) can be successfully related to various parameters such as axial cutting depth (Z), spindle speed (S), feed rate (F), and machining vibration (V_b) by a nonlinear model in the form of a power law formula:

$$Ra = CZ^{\beta_1} S^{\beta_2} F^{\beta_3} V_b^{\beta_4} \quad (1)$$

The power-law model can be expressed in logarithmic transformation form:

$$\ln Ra = \ln C + \beta_1 \ln Z + \beta_2 \ln S + \beta_3 \ln F + \beta_4 \ln V_b \quad (2)$$

The influences of the parameters and their interactions on the surface roughness were considered. The regression coefficients β_i ($i = 0, 1, 2$) are to be estimated from the experimental data by the method of least squares regression analysis.

B. Artificial Neural Network Model

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been recognized as a powerful tool to establish a high nonlinear correlation between dependent and independent variables and the interactive effects among variables. In this study, cutting parameters, such as spindle speed and cutting depth were selected at 8 and 7 levels, respectively. This eventually yields the nonlinear characteristic of the surface roughness with cutting parameters. Therefore, ANN modeling approach was employed to establish the predictive model of surface roughness [27-30]. A three layered ANN with one input layer, one hidden layer, and one output layer was considered the appropriate architecture to model the surface roughness during the machining process. The variables or the neuron used input layer are spindle speed, feed rate, axial cutting depth, and machining vibration of the spindle tool. The target to be predicted in the output layer is the surface roughness of the machined parts. The neuron in hidden layer provides the relationship between the input and the output layers and delivers the processed data from the neurons in the input layers to neurons in the output layer. A general form characterizing the relationship between input data and the neurons in the hidden layer is given by:

$$x_{hidden,j} = \sum_{i=1}^n W_{ij} u_i + \theta_j \quad (3)$$

where W_{ij} is the weight coefficient between the input and the hidden neurons, u_i is the value of the input, and θ_j denotes the biases of the hidden neurons.

The effectiveness of ANN models is dependent on various characteristics such as network architecture, activation functions, and training algorithms. Essentially, the Multilayer Perception (MLP) network was used to establish the predictive model, which was trained with the application of the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) method, conjugate gradient, and the steepest descent training algorithm. Another ANN network is the Radial Basis Function (RBF) network, which has equivalent capabilities to the MLP model, but with faster training [30]. To realize the best network, the activation functions—Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), tanh, logistic were chosen based on their ability to introduce non-linearity and facilitate learning complex patterns of the data. A trial and error scheme was used to determine the appropriate number of hidden neurons. Further, the error function was used to determine errors between the actual and the calculated values during learning, testing, and validation:

$$Errors = \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - t_i)^2 / N \quad (4)$$

The prediction performance of the regression models can be evaluated with the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), determination coefficient (R), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE):

$$RMSE = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - y_i)^2}{N} \right)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (t_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i)^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$MAPE = \sum_{i=1}^N ((t_i - y_i) / t_i) \times 100 / N \quad (7)$$

where t is the target value, y is the predicted value, and N is the number of samples.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Variation of Surface Roughness

Variations of the surface roughness with changing of cutting parameters are illustrated in Figure 3. In addition to fewer samples with significant roughness generated at certain cutting parameter value, the roughness value of all machined surfaces essentially ranges from 0.6 to 3.7 μm , depending on the cutting conditions used in machining. At specific speed, poor surface roughness was generated under a larger cutting depth (Figure 3(a)). At a certain cutting depth, there is no significant trend in the effect of spindle speed on the surface roughness, but it is clearly shown that when machining was conducted under speed between 6000 and 8000 rpm with cutting depth above 3.0 mm, the surface roughness increases significantly.

Fig. 3. Distribution of surface roughness under different cutting conditions: (a) speed and depth, (b) feed and depth.

Figure 3(b) shows the surface roughness generated at different feed rates and depths. Obviously, the surface finish produced under high feed rates ($> 2500 \text{ mm/min}$) and spindle speeds between 6000 and 8000 rpm is significantly worse. Similarly, the surface finish produced by high feed rates ($>2500 \text{ mm/min}$) and spindle speeds between 6000 and 8000 rpm is also significantly worse. Overall, the surface roughness increases as the depth of cut increases. A higher feed rate generates higher roughness on the machined surface, which means that the feed rate has a certain influence on the surface roughness. Basically, appropriate values of spindle speed, feed rate, and depth of cut can be selected to improve the machining quality and processing efficiency from the response surface plot against different combination of the cutting parameters.

B. Variation of Machining Vibration

Figure 4 shows the variation of the machining vibration generated at different cutting conditions. When the specific speed is 6000 to 8000 rpm and the depth of cut is above 3.0 mm, the vibration of the tool increases significantly, resulting in a significant increase in surface roughness. The same phenomenon of significant increase in tool vibration was observed for high feed rate ($> 2500 \text{ mm/min}$) and large depth of cut ($> 2.5 \text{ mm}$), affecting the machining quality with higher roughness value.

Fig. 4. Response surface of tool vibration under different conditions: (a) speed and depth, (b) depth and feed.

C. Regression Model of Surface Roughness

From the statistical analysis based on the experimental results, the influence of machining parameters and tool vibration on the surface quality of the workpiece was clearly examined. The statistical coefficients of regression analysis are shown in Tables II. The resulting regression equation of surface roughness is:

$$Ra = 20.345Z^{0.24585} S^{0.6628} F^{0.4907} V_b^{0.20573} \quad (8)$$

It should be noted that the regression model in explicit form clearly shows the influence of the individual parameters and their interactive effects on surface roughness. The spindle speed has a negative effect on roughness, while the cutting depth and feed rate show a positive influence. In other words, the roughness shows a tendency to increase with the increase of feed rate or cutting depth, but it decreases with increasing spindle speed. The scatter plots between the measured roughness and the predicted values of all 168 samples are shown in Figure 5, which indicates the close correlation between them. The correlation coefficient between the measured and the predicted values is around 0.79 and the average prediction error is 14.5%. The results demonstrate that the regression model based on cutting parameters (spindle speed, cutting depth, and feed rate) and machining vibration displays certain accuracy in predicting the surface roughness. This also indicates that the tool vibration induced in machining process substantially affects the surface quality of the machined parts.

TABLE II. REGRESSION PARAMETERS OF NONLINEAR POWER-LAW Ra MODEL

Parameter	Coefficient	Standard deviation	P-value
Intercept	3.01287	0.45928	6.81E-10
Cutting depth (Z)	0.24584	0.04472	1.46E-07
Spindle speed (S)	-0.6628	0.06959	2.25E-17
Feed rate (F)	0.49073	0.05326	1.52E-16
Vibration (V _b)	0.20577	0.02853	1.95E-11

Fig. 5. Comparison of the surface roughness between measurements and regression predictions.

D. ANN Predictive Model

A dataset collected from machining tests was used to create the ANN predictive models, in which 80% of the records were selected for model training, 10% of the records were used for testing, and the rest for validation. The ANN modeling was conducted utilizing MLP and RBF networks, respectively by Statistica Neural Networks software [31]. After many attempts, the ANN models were evaluated by observing prediction performance and correlation coefficient. In the MLP architecture, the activation functions, logistic and tanh are found to have good performance, enhancing the learning efficiency and accuracy. RBF networks typically have three layers: an input layer, a hidden layer with a non-linear activation function, and a linear output layer. To initialize the network, the weights are set to random values. Subsequently, through the application of a training algorithm, these weights are iteratively adjusted until they converge to specific values

employing the training algorithm and activation functions. This iterative process refines the network, enhancing its ability to accurately model and learn from the training data.

In this study, four ANN models with optimum performance were selected, as listed in Table III. The ANN models are labeled with the number of neurons in each layer, and the optimized number of neurons in the hidden layer. For example, MLP 4-14-1 and MLP 4-30-1, were optimized with 14 and 30 neurons in the hidden layer, respectively. The sensitivity levels of the constructed ANN input parameters are also given in Table III. Essentially, a parameter with small sensitivity value has more influence on the output parameter and a parameter with larger sensitivity value shows less influence. As a whole, the spindle speed has the larger sensitivity values.

TABLE III. SENSITIVITY LEVEL OF THE INPUT VARIABLES OF THE SELECTED ANN MODELS

ANN model	Sensitivity of input variables			
	Speed (rpm)	Feed (mm/min)	Depth (mm)	Vibration level (g)
MLP 4-14-1	6.687	5.540	4.014	2.278
MLP 4-16-1	7.506	7.473	4.697	2.877
MLP 4-22-1	5.370	5.290	5.792	3.649
MLP 4-30-1	5.453	5.032	5.407	2.194

Figure 6 depicts the variations of MSE values of the MLP network with the training cycles. It was found that MLP networks with activation functions tanh and logistic show similar learning efficiency with slow convergence performance (around 120 epochs). Both activation functions yield a good convergence to small prediction errors of about 0.002. Besides, the changes of error functions for training and testing dataset are relatively consistent. This indicates that there is no obvious over- or under-fitting problem in establishing MLP predictive models with tanh and logistic functions.

Fig. 6. Variations of the loss function of different MLP networks.

The variations of the MSE value of RBF networks with training cycles are shown in Figure 7. The RBF models show an efficient learning rate with fast convergence performance

(around 20-30 training cycles) which is faster than that of the MLP networks. According to the training results presented in Figures 6 and 7, both MLP and RBF models are well trained. However, the prediction error of RBF models is around 0.01, which is higher than that of the MLP models, indicating that the MLP network has better fitting capability to the dataset. In addition, the number of neurons slightly affects the convergence process. Basically, more neurons increase the complexity of the model, easily generating the over-fitting problem. But this phenomenon was not observed in the MLP and RBF models considered in this study. As seen in Table IV, the prediction performance of the ANN models does not reveal any substantial variation across different configurations of hidden neurons.

Fig. 7. Variations of the loss function of different RBF networks.

TABLE IV. STATISTICAL VALUES OF ANN MODELS

ANN model	Training dataset			Validation dataset			Testing dataset			Activation function	
	R	RMSE	MAPE	R	RMSE	MAPE	R	RMSE	MAPE	Hidden layer	Output layer
MLP 4-14-1	0.908	0.216	10.10%	0.897	0.298	11.80%	0.909	0.300	9.47%	Tanh	Logistic
MLP 4-16-1	0.902	0.222	11.64%	0.880	0.253	10.78%	0.937	0.290	11.54%	Logistic	Identity
MLP 4-22-1	0.900	0.224	10.73%	0.908	0.270	10.69%	0.928	0.270	9.99%	Tanh	Logistic
MLP 4-30-1	0.886	0.238	12.02%	0.910	0.297	9.64%	0.903	0.290	12.50%	Logistic	Identity
RBF 4-16-1	0.799	0.300	16.80%	0.816	0.330	20.80%	0.784	0.458	18.20%	Gaussian	Identity
RBF 4-30-1	0.781	0.310	15.30%	0.795	0.325	19.00%	0.782	0.447	17.90%	Gaussian	Identity

Fig. 8. Surface roughness value comparison between measurements and ANN predictions.

Figure 8 shows the comparison between the measured surface roughness and the predicted values of all samples, clearly indicating that roughness values predicted by the MLP models agree well with the measurements.

The prediction performance of the ANN models, evaluated in terms of determination coefficient R, RMSE, and MAPE, can be seen in Table IV. The values of R for the 4 MLP models with training, validation, and testing data are in the range 0.887–0.937, which means that for the selected ANN models, the MAPE of all datasets is about 9.47–12.5% and the RMSE around 0.21–0.30. Nevertheless, for the RBF models, the MAPE and RMSE values are around 15.3–20.8% and 0.3–0.458, respectively. Comparing the statistical values listed in Table IV, the MLP models have significantly higher prediction accuracy than the RBF models. This result indicates that the MLP network is more suitable for establishing a predictive model based on the collected dataset from the machining process with a wide range of cutting conditions. This conclusion is similar to the findings reported in [30]. In addition, comparisons of prediction accuracy of multiple regression models and ANN models clearly reveal that the ANN models provided better results with higher accuracy of around 90%.

E. Model Verification

Additional machining experiments were carried out to validate the prediction model of surface roughness. Cutting operation was processed under different speeds, cutting depths, and feed rates, which were defined in the high stable region based on the stability lobes diagram [17]. Details of the cutting parameters are given in Table V. It should be noted that the dataset collected for model verification was not included in model training. Surface roughness was measured for each machined surface. As illustrated in Figure 9, the surface roughness under cutting depth of 3.5 mm and speed of 5500 rpm was measured as 1.668 μm . For cutting depth of 2.5 mm at a speed of 7500 rpm, the measured Ra was 1.985 μm .

TABLE V. EXPERIMENT PARAMETERS AND THEIR LEVELS.

Parameter	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Spindle speed (<i>S</i> , rpm)	5500	7500	9500
Cutting depth, (<i>Z</i> , mm)	1.5	2.5	3.5
Feed rate, (<i>F</i> , mm/min)	0.05	0.075	0.1

The roughness values obtained by prediction and measurement are summarized in Table VI, which also

compares the prediction results of regression models and the selected ANN models.

TABLE VI. DATASET FOR MODEL VERIFICATION

No	Cutting parameters			Measured vibration	Measured Ra (μm)	Predicted Ra (μm)	
	Depth	Speed	Feed			Power law	ANN model
1	1.5	5500	2200	0.026	1.59	1.54	1.63
2	2.5	5500	2200	0.051	1.92	2.00	2.09
3	3.5	5500	2200	0.087	2.45	2.43	2.57
4	1.5	7500	3000	0.071	1.98	1.79	2.13
5	2.5	7500	3000	0.068	2.07	2.01	2.16
6	3.5	7500	3000	0.063	2.19	2.16	2.17
7	1.5	9500	3800	0.027	1.64	1.41	1.51
8	2.5	9500	3800	0.050	1.97	1.82	1.80
9	3.5	9500	3800	0.068	2.21	2.10	2.11
10	1.5	5500	1650	0.023	1.19	1.30	1.27
11	2.5	5500	1650	0.036	1.44	1.62	1.49
12	3.5	5500	1650	0.052	1.67	1.90	1.73
13	1.5	7500	2250	0.057	1.46	1.49	1.43
14	2.5	7500	2250	0.079	1.99	1.81	1.87
15	3.5	7500	2250	0.121	2.60	2.14	2.58
16	1.5	9500	2850	0.030	1.29	1.25	1.18
17	2.5	9500	2850	0.065	1.56	1.67	1.43
18	3.5	9500	2850	0.074	1.64	1.86	1.67
19	1.5	5500	1100	0.018	1.01	1.02	0.88
20	2.5	5500	1100	0.022	1.01	1.21	1.02
21	3.5	5500	1100	0.031	1.10	1.40	1.19
22	1.5	7500	1500	0.035	1.17	1.11	0.87
23	2.5	7500	1500	0.052	1.49	1.36	1.43
24	3.5	7500	1500	0.063	1.88	1.53	1.50
25	1.5	9500	1900	0.021	0.98	0.96	0.93
26	2.5	9500	1900	0.047	1.35	1.28	1.02
27	3.5	9500	1900	0.055	1.66	1.43	1.19
					MAPE	8.87%	8.11%
					RMSE	0.179	0.169
					R	0.916	0.946

regression models can predict roughness with high prediction accuracy of about 92%. Basically, the ANNs can generate different models based on the training data and training algorithm, yielding different prediction results. The number of neurons in the hidden layer will affect the prediction error and overall prediction performance. The verification tests again demonstrate that the established predictive models based on the machining parameters and vibration assessed from the milling process can accurately forecast the surface roughness generated at various cutting conditions.

Fig. 10. Surface roughness comparison between measurements and predictions.

Fig. 9. Surface morphologies and vibration spectrum.

As shown in Figure 10, the correlation coefficients for ANN and regression models range between 0.946 and 0.916, which means that the predictions are in good agreement with the measurements for the verification dataset. Besides, based on MAPE and RMSE values, it is found that the ANN and

V. CONSTRUCTION OF THE MONITORING SYSTEM

In order to achieve online machining monitoring and real-time prediction, the processing parameters must be obtained from a controller. At present, the VMX intelligent software development platform developed by the Industrial Technology Research Institute in Taiwan can be connected to different controllers. The monitoring APPs developed with C language were implemented on the IIOT-VMX system in an industrial PC, including the data processing module and the surface roughness predictive model. The cutting parameters and various servo parameters in the controller can be easily accessed through the OPCUA communication interface. In addition, the machining vibration can be acquired from the accelerometers mounted on the spindle through a data acquisition device. The surface roughness model can be established through ANNs or regression analysis for model training and verification. In the milling process, the processing parameters and real-time vibration signals and features, which were fed as inputs into the prediction model, were directly extracted and processed. As illustrated in Figure 11, the user can preset the desired roughness and threshold of the vibration levels. The cutting parameters assessed from the controller and the time domain vibration levels in the 3 axes are simultaneously displayed on the screen. To monitor the variation of machining quality during the milling process, the

system continuously outputs the roughness based on the input parameters with vibration features. At the same time, the system will issue an alert signal when the predicted roughness exceeds the threshold or vibration abnormalities are detected.

Fig. 11. Schematics of the surface quality monitoring system and the visualization interface.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to develop an online surface quality monitoring system, attempting to predict the variation of the surface roughness based on the cutting parameters and the vibration features during milling machining. Based on the acquired results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The cutting parameters for establishing the prediction model should be defined within the stable boundaries of the stability lobes diagram. This can ensure practical applicability for a variety of cutting process from low speed rough machining to high speed finishing machining.
- A surface roughness predictive model can be well developed by regression analysis with nonlinear power-law function or an MLP network with adequate defined training algorithm and activation functions, yielding superior prediction accuracy about 90%.
- The vibration assessed from the machine tool is a critical factor influencing surface roughness. It should be integrated along with the cutting parameters in the predictive model of the surface quality of the machined parts.
- The predictive model and the data processing module were integrated into the IIOT-VMX platform. This platform facilitates direct assessments of cutting parameters through the OPCUA interface and captures vibration features via a

sensory module on the spindle tool. Subsequent testing results demonstrated the system's effectiveness, establishing its potential as an online surface quality monitoring system for practical machining processes.

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Numeric Validation of the Inversion Model of Electrical Resistivity Imaging Method using the Levenberg-Marquardt Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a new application of the Electrical Resistivity Imaging (ERI) method within the realm of structural assessment, deviating from its conventional use in geology. The study presents an innovative inversion model that incorporates the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, representing a notable leap in seamlessly integrating ERI into structural analysis. Rigorous validation of the inversion methodology is conducted through extensive benchmarking against simulated reference data, focusing on 1D and 2D resistivity distributions within timber specimens. By utilizing known resistivity fields, the paper quantitatively validates the accuracy of reconstructed models obtained through numerical simulations. Notably, both longitudinal and transverse surveys exhibit exceptional outcomes, showcasing a high correlation with the actual resistivity profiles, achieved within a concise 10-13 iterations. This meticulous validation process conclusively underscores the effectiveness and precision of the proposed inversion approach. Beyond its scientific contribution, this research expands the conventional boundaries of ERI application and establishes it as an invaluable tool for structural monitoring.

Keywords-ERI; inversion model; resistivity; Levenberg-Marquardt; numeric validation

I. INTRODUCTION

Electrical Resistivity Imaging (ERI) is a highly effective geophysical technique employed for mapping subsurface variations in both lateral and vertical electrical resistivity [1-3]. This method involves deploying arrays of electrodes on the ground surface to inject current and measure potential differences within the subsurface. The systematic arrangement of electrodes in the ground is crucial for the subsurface resistivity assessment. The measurement process involves applying a precisely measured direct current or low-frequency alternating current (denoted as I_{AB}) between electrodes A and B . Subsequently, the voltage of the alternating current (denoted as ΔV_{MN}) is measured between the remaining electrodes M and N , which serve as potential electrodes. Apparent resistivity data collected along survey lines are processed and inverted to produce 2D and 3D models of true resistivity distribution. ERI has wide applicability for near surface investigations related to civil infrastructure, hydrogeology, environmental assessment, and archeology due to its ability to differentiate materials based on electrical properties. Factors such as mineral composition, porosity, water content, and salt concentration influence field measurements [4, 5]. By detecting electrical property contrasts, ERI can delineate subsurface lithological contacts, solution cavities, contaminant plumes, and structural features without cumbersome drilling [2, 6]. ERI is also employed for structural health monitoring of concrete and timber elements. Variations in moisture content, cracks, and defects create contrasts in

electrical conductivity that are mapped through inversion of the resistivity data. This allows accurate identification of internal damage in concrete caused by corrosion, leakage, or erosion [7, 8]. For timber, ERI enables differentiation of moisture gradients and decay pockets based on resistivity contrasts without extensive drilling [9]. The sensitivity of ERI to subtle changes in electrical properties allows early detection of latent defects and deterioration prior to visual manifestations on the structural.

In geophysics, the Res2Dinv software facilitates the computation of the projected resistivity field onto the study area using apparent resistivity values measured in the field [6, 10]. This calculation relies on an inverse method that minimizes the difference between experimental measurements and apparent resistivities derived from numerical computations. The underlying principle, termed inversion, assumes point injection into a semi-infinite medium, which is notably unrealistic in this context due to the limited and confined structural dimensions in space. This paper develops an inversion model that allows for considering the actual geometry of the studied volumes.

II. THE LEVENBERG-MARQUARDT ALGORITHM AND ITS APPLICATION TO THE ELECTRICAL RESISTIVITY OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Levenberg-Marquardt is an effective algorithm for nonlinear regression models [11-13]. It strategically combines

Gradient Descent [14, 15] and Gauss-Newton approaches [16, 17]. When parameters are distant from the optimal values, the algorithm leverages a Gradient Descent-like search to approach global optimum territory while avoiding entrapment in suboptimal local extrema. As the solution trajectory nears putative optima, the technique transitions to exploit Gauss-Newton's rapid fine-scale convergence properties. This blended approach confers multiple advantages over pure Gradient Descent. By prioritizing global exploration initially, Levenberg-Marquardt avoids stagnation in local minima. The subsequent activation of Gauss-Newton's efficient local search allows precision-tuning of parameters to expedite convergence at optimized coordinates. However, disadvantages include substantially greater computational overhead versus basic Gradient Descent, as well as more intricate algorithmic implementation. $d = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_N\}$ represents the measured data (with N being the number of measurements), and $m = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_M\}$ represents the model parameters (with M being the number of parameters). So, the model function is: $f = f(m)$.

According to the least squares method, the expression of the difference between measured and calculated data, or also referred to as the objective function F is then expressed in the following matrix form:

$$F = (\Delta d - J\Delta m)^T \cdot (\Delta d - J\Delta m) \quad (1)$$

In this context, Δd denotes the variance between the measured and computed data. The inversion outcomes converge towards adjusting the initial model m_0 through a correction Δm .

$$\Delta d = d - f(m_0) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta m = m - m_0 \quad (3)$$

The Jacobian matrix encodes localized gradient information to guide optimization algorithms towards minimizing model-data misfit. Its size matches observations by parameters, with elements quantifying parameter influence on each data point. For nonlinear inverse problems, iterative methods successively update parameters along the Jacobian-indicated descent direction.

$$J_{ij} = \frac{\partial f(m_i)}{m_j} \quad (4)$$

The correction vector is thus defined by:

$$\Delta m = (J^T J + \lambda W_m)^{-1} J^T \Delta d \quad (5)$$

The damping parameter λ enables regularization of the approximation to the Hessian matrix $J^T J$ utilized during inversion, mitigating ill-conditioning via addition of a scalar value to the eigenvalues. Conceptually, λ mediates the tradeoff between resolution and accuracy in the inverse problem solution. Excessive damping magnitudes prolong

inversion execution. However, the resultant models can demonstrate improved fidelity. Conversely, reduced λ values prioritize efficient convergence over precision. Accordingly, common Levenberg-Marquardt implementations allow dynamic tuning of λ : decreasing the damping factor when the objective function shows decreasing misfit to accelerate mapping, while increasing λ to restore stabilization upon divergence. The modulated attenuation introduced by the damping parameter therefore facilitates adaptive control over convergence and precision. Further analysis of automated, data-driven λ selection is warranted to optimize the balance between model accuracy and computational efficiency.

In the electrical inversion problem, the vector m is defined as the conductivity, and the resistivity is determined as the reciprocal of m .

$$m_{\text{resistivity}} = \left\{ \frac{1}{m_1}, \frac{1}{m_2}, \dots, \frac{1}{m_M} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The key to the inverse problem lies in the selection of M . A larger value of M leads to a more accurate electrical resistivity field, however, an increase in M may render the inverse problem resource-intensive and potentially unsolvable. Therefore, this paper proposes dividing the sample into M elements with constant electrical resistivity within each element. The vector m comprises components that represent the conductivity values of the M elements. The measured $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ can be represented in the form of a vector d which is called the measured data vector. N represents the number of measurements dictated by the multiplexing. The direct problem is then defined as a function $f(m)$ whose result is expressed in the form of a vector composed of the $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ values computed by the direct model.

III. NUMERIC VALIDATION OF THE INVERSION MODEL

A. Details of the Numerical Inversion Validation Process

1) Initial Resistivity Model

An initial homogeneous resistivity model m_0 is defined, with a value reasonably approximating known subsurface conditions.

2) Parameterization

The model domain is discretized into M elements of homogeneous resistivity values to be estimated through inversion.

3) Forward Modeling

For a given m , the numerical direct model predicts the array voltage response $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$. An accurate simulation of the true subsurface electric field is required.

4) Inversion

An iterative optimization algorithm adjusts the resistivity model to minimize the misfit between measured and modeled $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$, generating a correction vector d at each iteration based on the Levenberg-Marquardt method.

5) Convergence

Inversion terminates once predefined stopping criteria are met relating model parameters, misfit error, and number of iterations. If convergence fails, regularization parameters and discretization can be adjusted. Final modeled resistivities comprise the inverted section. The validation process for the inversion model involves utilizing data resolved by the direct model, which are subsequently introduced into the inverse model as "measured data". Knowledge of the true resistivity field permits the validation of the inversion model. This article builds upon the direct finite element model developed in [9] which enables simulating the multiplexed measurement algorithm coupling the resolution of Ohm's law (current injection and electric potential calculation) with a multiplexing procedure concordant with the measurement configuration. For any given resistivity field, the model can determine the numerical values of $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ when measured with different multiplexers. The validation of the inversion model is carried out in two cases: (1) Longitudinal resistivity profile and (2) traverse resistivity profile.

B. Case 1: Longitudinal Resistivity Profile

This problem is based on the assumption of a homogeneous resistivity distribution on the traverse section. Consider a timber specimen with dimensions of $320 \times 95 \times 95 \text{ mm}^3$ and 21 inline electrodes spaced by 15 mm in an array along the length of the specimen as shown in Figure 1. Cylindrical metal electrodes with a diameter of 2 mm are inserted into the sample to a depth of 10 mm.

Fig. 1. Dimensions of the specimen and electrode arrangement for the case 1 model.

This study uses a dipole-dipole quadrupole configuration, which allows obtaining a very low electromagnetic coupling between the current and potential lines while giving a high density of measurement points (Figure 2). Consider a resistivity field with a gradient shape varying from 10^4 to $10^6 \Omega\text{m}$ as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. Dipole - dipole configuration.

Fig. 3. The electrical resistivity field of case 1 into the direct model.

The current injection in forward modeling is simulated using three types of dipole-dipole quadrupole arrays by varying the n values successively to $n = 1$ (type 1), $n = 2$ (type 2), and $n = 3$ (type 3), allowing for the determination of a total of 51 numeric values of $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$. These 51 values are used as the "measured data" fed into the inverse model to determine the resistivity field of the specimen. In this case, the known resistivity field beforehand allows validating the accuracy of the inversion model.

C. Case 2: Traverse Resistivity Profile

The specimen is a cubic prism with dimensions of $95 \times 95 \times 95 \text{ mm}^3$. In this case, the approach is generalized to an electrode arrangement in the form of a belt. Five electrodes per face are spaced 15 mm apart, in a two-dimensional configuration (Figure 4). In contrast to the previous one-dimensional case, all quadrupole configurations are exploited. This makes it possible to investigate the entire cross-section and achieve a high density of measurement points, not only on the surface but also inside the core. Two multiplexing processes are implemented per measurement: Multiplexing 1 sweeps electrodes 1 through 20, multiplexing 2 sweeps electrodes 10 to 11 (Figure 5).

Fig. 4. Dimensions of the specimen and electrode arrangement for the case 2 model.

Fig. 5. Two electrical measurement directions of case 2 specimen.

The goal is to determine the resistivity distribution in a cross-section of the sample. The hypothesis of constant resistivity, along the longitudinal direction, is then proposed. Similar to the longitudinal case, we consider an example of an exponentially varying resistivity profile from 10^4 to $10^6 \Omega m$ as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. The electrical resistivity field of case 2 into the direct model.

Multiplexing (Figure 5) produces 319 values of $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$.

These values are used as the "measured data" fed into the inverse model to determine the resistivity field of the specimen.

D. The Inverse Problem-solving Process

In Case 1, the sample is segmented into 10 equal-length segments, while in Case 2, it is discretized into a grid of 5×5 elements. Each segment in Case 1 and each element in Case 2 is characterized by a homogeneous resistivity value (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Coarse meshing for the implementation of the inversion model.

Let us choose the initial condition m_0 as a homogeneous electrical resistivity of $10^7 \Omega m$. Since the function f_m is

essentially the direct model, the values of the Jacobian matrix cannot be directly computed through differentiation. Therefore, an approximate calculation method is proposed:

$$J_{ij} = \frac{f_i(m_j + \Delta m_j) - f_i(m_j)}{\Delta m_j} \tag{7}$$

The regularization parameter λ is dynamically selected during the inversion process. The first iteration starts with a sufficiently high λ_0 value relative to the Jacobian matrix terms, to ensure stability. For subsequent iterations, λ is updated based on the change in objective function: it is reduced by a factor α if the objective function decreases (indicating convergence) or increased by a factor β otherwise. Direct matrix inversion utilizes partial pivoting Gaussian factorization. The stopping criterion is based on the parameter variation between two successive iteration $i+1$ and i falls below a threshold f_m , as defined in (8):

$$\left| \frac{m_{i+1} - m_i}{m_i} \right| \leq f_m \tag{8}$$

In this case, we choose $\lambda_0 = 10^{16}$, $\alpha = 0.1$, and $\beta = 10$, with the stopping criterion set to $f_m = 10^{-3}$.

For Case 1, the time required for each iteration is less than 15 min. The inversion procedure stops after 12 iterations. The mean absolute discrepancy between measured and inverted $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ values is 6.8%. By comparing the differences between

measured and inverted $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$, in the bulk region, the inversion yields promising results, however, near the sample edges, where the current lines are constrained, the algorithm lacks efficiency (Figure 8). Ultimately, the mesh density has to be compatible with the richness of information - sparser towards the edges compared to the central region.

The thickness of the two segments at the edges is selected as 4 cm, while the bulk region is discretized into 8 segments with equal thickness values of 3cm (Figure 9).

Fig. 8. Relative error between measured and estimated $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ resulting from the Case 1 discretization into 10 equal-thickness segments.

Fig. 9. Coarse meshing of the Case 1 specimen with unequal-thickness segments.

The inversion procedure terminates after 10 iterations. The inverted resistivity model exhibits a commendable correlation with the true resistivity distribution, as confirmed by a small deviation (0.05%) between the measured and predicted $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ responses (Figure 10). Thus, it can be observed that employing a grid division aligned with the measured density region enables the determination of the corresponding appropriate electrical resistivity field.

Fig. 10. Relative error between measured and estimated $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ resulting from the Case 1 discretization into 10 unequal-thickness segments.

For Case 2, each iteration takes 55 min with the inversion stopping at the 12th iteration. The difference between the measured and estimated $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ is less than 0.5% on average.

Figure 11 indicates that the errors of the 3 types of dipole-dipole and quadrupole configurations are smaller than those of the remaining quadrupoles.

Through the two considered examples, it can be concluded that the inverse model constructed using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm was able provide reliable results.

Fig. 11. Relative error between measured and estimated $\frac{\Delta V_{MN}}{I_{AB}}$ resulting from the Case 2 resolution.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper presented a method of employing the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm for electricity resistivity inversion. The article proposed a strategy for selecting the lambda coefficient based on the magnitude of the Jacobian matrix, with the additional adjustment of increasing or decreasing coefficients by a factor of 10 to ensure algorithm convergence and efficient problem-solving. The paper also outlined an approximate method for calculating the Jacobian matrix since computing derivatives becomes impractical when utilizing the direct model as the model function.

Furthermore, the development of the inverse model and its validation were elucidated, utilizing numerical data from the direct model as simulated measurement values. This validation approach involves comparing the obtained results with pre-known resistivity field values, affirming the accuracy of the inverse model. Applying the inversion algorithm to map resistivity distributions in timber specimens, specifically addressing 1D and 2D resistivity profiles (longitudinal and traverse), has showcased the accuracy of the inverse model. After 10-13 iterations, the inverse model yielded results with an error below 1% for both cases, thus confirming the effectiveness of the inversion approach.

While these 1D and 2D examples show promising outcomes for the inversion algorithm, integrating real-world experimental data into the validation phase is crucial for reinforcing the robustness and reliability of the proposed method. Further experimentation and verification in actual field conditions are essential steps to validate the practical applicability of the presented approach.

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Assessing the Level of Maturity of Operational Excellence in Morocco: A Comparative Study between SMEs and LEs

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, excellence is the ultimate goal for every company wishing to improve and lead the market. The focus is on ensuring that any product or service meets certain criteria, leading to total perfection. This article aims to shed light on operational excellence in Morocco. A form was distributed to 40 firms operating in different sectors in Morocco, to assess the level of maturity of Operational Excellence (OpEx) dimensions. A comparative study was carried out between Small-Medium (SMEs) and Large (LEs) Enterprises. For each company size, a specific result can be distinguished. This assessment of OpEx maturity levels gives a general idea of the level of perfection of these firms operating in Morocco. The results differ according to size, and each dimension of OpEx was a subject of study.

Keywords-excellence; operational excellence; assessment; dimensions

I. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

An excellent company is one that aims to achieve the highest level of performance with the tools it possesses. An excellent company today cannot generally remain on the path to excellence without a real vision of the future and a prior knowledge of the competitive challenges faced by different companies operating in the same sector or implementing the same tools and enabling them to perfect a given product or service. The term Operational Excellence (OpEx) is a very topical one, and leads us to ask ourselves what means we really have to achieve industrial excellence. A first definition of this purely industrial term leads us to focus on optimizing the four criteria of excellence to the maximum: cost, quality, lead time, and service. Sometimes, it is essential to think about the cost of production as a major criterion, or as a requirement of a particular customer. Often, the question is whether we can ensure the right delivery of a particular product at the right time. The term OpEx comes into play here, and brings the four criteria together with a view to optimizing them as far as possible in the short term. We always check whether we can use the right means to achieve our goal, because the criteria for excellence change as customer requirements change. The aim of this article is to shed some light on the term operational excellence. We are more interested in assessing the level of maturity of OpEx in Morocco. We want to know whether the

companies in Morocco have what it takes to improve and lead the market.

Regarding OpEx in terms of performance, authors in [1] were interested in improving the performance of a Microstrip Antenna by adding a slot into different patch designs. Authors in [2] evaluated the performance of the BLDC motor using nonlinear model predictive control. The aim in [3] was to revisit the performance of spectral clustering algorithms for water distribution networks. Authors in [4] clearly defined the term OpEx as having a deep focus on embedding efficiency in the company. We achieve this by optimizing processes, reducing overhead costs, eliminating steps, etc. Authors in [5] provided a comprehensive review of OpEx. Authors in [6] aimed to provide a comprehensive approach to measuring OpEx. Authors in [7] presented the most critical reasons for failure of OpEx initiatives. Within Nepalese industries, the sustainability of firms that complete OpEx in their own way was verified in [8]. Authors in [9] gave an OpEx framework. In order to achieve OpEx, we must first reach a high level of maturity in every of its dimensions.

Considering the cost as a major criterion for achieving OpEx, authors in [10] discussed an evaluation of cost optimization strategies for BRT projects in Pakistan. Authors in [11] considered blockchain technology and its major role in ensuring OpEx sustainability for a perishable food supply chain. Turning to service firms in Jordan, authors in [12]

proposed a series of critical factors that affect OpEx. Authors in [13] were interested in giving the methods needed to integrate sustainable OpEx into any industrial firm. The work in [14] was based on two case studies, one in Brazil and another in Scotland, that were always looking to improve the performance of sustainable supply chains through new approaches of OpEx. Authors in [15] developed an OpEx framework. Authors in [16] showed the factors influencing OpEx of SMEs in Malaysia. Authors in [17] discussed the factors that can affect OpEx in the service sector and proposed a theoretical framework for this need. In [18], a survey was distributed to 106 experts in various countries implementing OpEx. The aim was to draw out the reasons for failure to achieve sustainable OpEx within these organizations. Authors in [19] discussed the CSFs leading to successful OpEx implementation in a manufacturing environment. Authors in [20] showed us the relationship between OpEx and management in the Malaysian context. The 8 elements of the OpEx program reported in [21] can be seen in Table I.

TABLE I. ELEMENTS OF THE OPEX PROGRAM [21]

Element	Meaning
Results	Expected results
Leadership	Ensuring a better working relationship
Requirements	Quality requirements as an example
Program definition	The steps to be taken from this program are followed
Supporting practices and procedures	Any practice or procedure that leads straight to the goal
Working culture	Smooth teamwork
Information management	Smooth information management
Follow-up	For a continuous improvement

To well-explain that, every requirement must be met to obtain the best possible end results. When it comes to production schedules, it is best to think in terms of daily, weekly, or even monthly schedules, to ensure that production flows smoothly within a given company. It is also essential to anticipate the expected result, which we must well define from the outset. We need also to master the right production tools. When it comes to a work culture that conforms to standards, we need to think about training our work teams, just as we need to respect well-defined work regulations from the outset. Having a work culture at the outset will improve the company's production output by reducing conflicts between staff and making teamwork more enjoyable. We must also ensure a smooth flow of information, facilitating access to information at all times. Periodic monitoring of production performance is just as important as financial monitoring, which is required at all times. The purpose can play a fundamental role in an OpEx approach. Ideally, we need to know the nature of the customer's request, and we need to think carefully about who needs to be involved in the follow-up of this approach. A process that transforms inputs into outputs should itself be of interest. Preserving gains and ultimately promoting the project as a whole are two points that we must essentially take into account when getting involved in this approach. Neglecting one of the 8 elements of OpEx can have undesired effect. That is why, when we embark on an OpEx approach, we need to take into account each of those elements.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Sampling Technique

For our quantitative research, we designed a form and collected the data via the internet, using the LinkedIn network. According to [22] four major modes of data administration are often used: (a) Administration by post, (b) administration via the internet, (c) face to face, and (d) administration by phone. Our research methodology is based first and foremost on the development of a measurement scale for the culture of OpEx. We put 24 questions to measure the level of OpEx maturity. The main objective was to identify the real maturity level of OpEx. Eight sub-components of Opex were considered, according to the elements of Table I [21].

B. Maturity Level of OpEx

Each concept or component was considered as the mean result of its sub-components [23].

$$\text{OpEx} = (\text{Results} + \text{Leadership} + \text{Requirements} + \text{Program definition} + \text{Supporting practices and procedures} + \text{Working culture} + \text{Information management} + \text{Follow-up}) / 8$$

C. OpEx Dimensions

TABLE II. OPEX TOOLS

Dimension	Wording	Items
Results	RES1	We always anticipate expected results
	RES2	An expected result is well defined at the outset
	RES3	We generally master the right means to achieve an expected result
Leadership	LDP1	We have full control over the direction of production turnover
	LDP2	Management is well aware of its duties and commitments towards customers
Requirements	REQ1	Product quality requirements are strictly adhered
	REQ2	Customer requirements are strictly met
	REQ3	A document clarifying all requirements is always present in the company
Program definition	PRD1	A daily production schedule is well defined within the company
	PRD2	A weekly production schedule is well defined at the outset
	PRD3	A monthly production schedule is well defined at the outset
Supporting practices and procedures	SPC1	We always use the right production tools
	SPC2	Innovation in support practices and procedures is fundamental to the company
Working culture	WCL1	We often train work teams
	WCL2	Work regulations are well respected
	WCL3	We work together in the right environment
	WCL4	We help each other with no strings attached
	WCL5	Absences and disputes at work are intolerable at some level
Information management	IFM1	Information management is well mastered from the outset
	IFM2	Easy access to information at all times
	IFM3	All information management facilitates the smooth running of tasks
Follow-up	FLU1	The production sequence is continued periodically
	FLU2	We demand financial monitoring at all times
	FLU3	Periodic monitoring of production output is required

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We looked at the number of employees within companies. We found that 20 were large, 4 medium-sized, and 16 small.

TABLE III. NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES

		Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Large	250 or more	20	50.0	50.0	50.0
Medium	50-249	4	10.0	10.0	60.0
Small	Less than 50	16	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	40	100.0	100.0	

A. Assessment of OpEx Maturity Level at SMEs

The maturity level results regarding Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) can be seen in Table IV.

TABLE IV. ASSESSMENT OF OPEX MATURITY LEVEL OF SMEs BY DIMENSION

Dimension	Maturity Level	Expected Maturity	Gap
Results	2.7	3.00	-0.3
Leadership	3.25	3.00	+0.25
Requirements	3.43	3.00	+0.43
Program definition	3.32	3.00	+0.32
Supporting practices and procedures	3.37	3.00	+0.37
Working culture	3.11	3.00	+0.11
Information management	3.1	3.00	+0.1
Follow-up	2.42	3.00	-0.58

Six results (leadership, requirements, program definition, supporting practices and procedures, working culture and information management) show that the maturity level of the OpEx dimensions is above average. These results confirm with certainty that an optimal level of OpEx is achieved for the six OpEx dimensions mentioned above. To better visualize the results, we have designed the graphical radar of Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Opex maturity level and expected maturity at SMEs.

B. Assessment of OpEx maturity level at Les

The maturity level results regarding Large Enterprises (SMEs) can be seen in Table IV. These data show an above average level of maturity for all the 8 dimensions of OpEx. The maximum maturity level is 4 for requirements and the minimum is 3.3 for follow-up. To better visualize the results, we have designed the graphical radar of Figure 2.

TABLE V. ASSESSMENT OF OPEX MATURITY LEVEL OF LES BY DIMENSION

Dimension	Maturity Level	Expected Maturity	Gap
Results	3.75	3.00	+0.75
Leadership	3.7	3.00	+0.7
Requirements	4	3.00	+1.00
Program definition	3.78	3.00	+0.78
Supporting practices and procedures	3.52	3.00	+0.52
Working culture	3.65	3.00	+0.65
Information management	3.62	3.00	+0.62
Follow-up	3.3	3.00	+0.3

Fig. 2. Opex maturity level and expected maturity of LES

C. Comparison of OpEx Maturity Levels between SMEs and LES

The results show an above-average level of maturity of all OpEx dimensions for LES. In the case of SMEs, only two OpEx dimensions have a maturity level below the average. The table below compares the OpEx maturity levels of SME and Le.

TABLE VI. OPEX MATURITY LEVEL COMPARISON

Dimension	SMEs maturity level	LEs maturity level	Gap
Results	2.7	3.75	+1.05
Leadership	3.25	3.7	+0.45
Requirements	3.43	4	+0.57
Program definition	3.32	3.78	+0.46
Supporting practices and procedures	3.37	3.52	+0.15
Working culture	3.11	3.65	+0.54
Information management	3.1	3.62	+0.52
Follow-up	2.42	3.3	+0.88

Fig. 3. Comparison of OpEx maturity levels between SMEs and LES.

A comparison of the maturity levels of SMEs and LES in Morocco reveals a number of points. A positive difference in the results of the 8 OpEx dimensions is obtained, with a

maximum value of 1.05 for results and a minimum of 0.15 for supporting practices and procedures. The results show that LEs have a higher level of maturity than SMEs. The difference can even be seen on the graphic radar of Figure 3.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study makes investigated the maturity level of operational excellence (OpEx) dimensions in Moroccan companies. The findings provide empirical evidence that the size has a significant impact on determining the maturity level of key OpEx dimensions like results, leadership, requirements, and procedures. The results were found to be in the same direction with the previous research. However, the limitations of a small localized sample affect the generalizability of the findings. Future studies can build on this work by incorporating larger and more diverse samples of Moroccan manufacturers. Comparative research between different developing economies may also offer valuable cross-cultural insights. Regarding the limitations of our research methodology, future research may raise questions other than those related to our research form. Overall, this study represents an early empirical effort to elucidate the maturity level of OpEx, providing a useful foundation for further research on this important issue. As we have already concluded, the first step is to know or highlight all the sub-dimensions of OpEx. We conclude from this study of 40 industrial firms in Morocco, that an above-average level of OpEx maturity is obtained for all dimensions of OpEx from all large firms (LEs) belonging to different sectors in Morocco. On the other hand, only 2 OpEx dimensions for Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are below average. Comparing the two company sizes, we conclude that an OpEx maturity level is reached and its average was exceeded for the LEs, which is not the case for all OpEx dimensions for SMEs.

OpEx remains an ultimate goal for every company aiming to increase productivity and improve production output in the short, medium, and long term. For some, it is all about staying ahead of the competition, while for others it is about leading the market. This goal of excellence certainly remains unique. For SMEs, staying on this competitive path is already a goal. For LEs, competition is ruthless, and they certainly want to dominate the market with any method or tool. This path to excellence may differ from one company to another. Of course, if we are to achieve concrete results, we really need to think about the opinions of the managers of the target companies. A goal of future research could be a field study on employees working for different companies in Morocco. The aim would be to find out what managers and workers think about this path of excellence. Comparing the acquired results, a positive difference is highlighted for all 8 OpEx dimensions and the maturity level for LEs is higher than that of SMEs operating in the different sectors. The added value of this article is to show that the size plays a fundamental role in determining OpEx maturity levels, and this is confirmed with certainty. We all play by the rules and aim for excellence, especially the larger firms.

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The Feasibility Study Report as an Effective Tool to Evaluate Investment Projects: A Solid Waste Treatment Project as a Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Hundreds of infrastructure investment projects are inserted into the Iraqi government budget annually. Many of these projects suffer from suspension, delay in completion, corruption, or other negative issues known in Iraqi construction projects. This may harm the country's economic recovery due to allocating funds to useless projects from one or more feasibility studies' components. Therefore, the best solution is to pay attention to the feasibility study reports. This study highlights the importance of feasibility studies reports for investment projects and their effective role in evaluating project ideas to ensure an equitable distribution of a country's financial resources to the most feasible investment projects. This importance was highlighted through a practical case study for a solid waste treatment project. The results of the case study showed that feasibility studies provide very important information on which investors and governments can rely to make the appropriate decisions for investment projects. The study also addressed the risks that investors can be exposed to in Iraq and how to include them in the economic analysis of feasibility studies.

Keywords- feasibility study; project management; investment; solid waste; energy

I. INTRODUCTION

In Iraq, many investment projects do not achieve the goals and assumptions on which they were based [1-2], not only because these assumptions were based on incorrect facts, but also because decision-makers did not deal efficiently with the uncertainty associated with each stage or every detail of the project. This failure may waste public money and prevent funding investment projects beneficial to the country [3-4]. Feasibility Studies (FSs) effectively reduce uncertainty by answering all the questions of investors and decision-makers by providing a scientific and logical analysis of real data or hypotheses close to reality [5]. An FS is a thorough investigation into the viability of an idea or concept that could affect the country's economic growth and its business potential. It is carried out to the point where the potential project is socially responsible, technically possible, commercially viable, and has a feasible business opportunity exit. The predominant perspective in the construction industry suggests that construction stakeholders prioritize maximizing profits during the execution phase of any project [6-7]. FS is a crucial and consequential aspect in the building industry and other technical domains, as it greatly influences investment decision-

making. Valuable feasibility studies are necessary for each construction project to obtain precise decisions from decision-makers or contractual parties, such as clients, consultants, and contractors. FSs conducted in the project initiation phase before significant expenses should deal with correct facts, assumptions, and up-to-date financial data. Every firm wants to succeed and improve its performance [8]. FSs have been identified as a key factor in achieving such a crucial goal. Many projects and business organizations have failed to achieve this goal because they do not begin or understand the implications of conducting FSs. This study investigates the effect of FSs on the evaluation process of investment project ideas and highlights its importance in providing the required answers for investors and decision-makers, converting uncertainty aspects to data close to certainty.

II. FEASIBILITY STUDY CONCEPT

An FS can be interpreted as an assessment of what can or cannot be effective at the conceptual stage of a project [9]. The FS report is an analysis of the viability of an idea. It is used in project management to discover potential positive and negative consequences before investing considerable time and money [10]. Therefore, an FS is an examination and evaluation of a

complicated nature at the level of future investment objectives over a set time frame, considering risks and uncertainties [11]. In [12], FS was defined as a technique for predicting the results of an investigation or evaluation of a proposed project and its potential benefits. An FS report can be considered the most common way to gather comprehensive and transparent data and results to assess the viability of an investment proposal [8, 13]. The purposes of FS are linked through the planning process to the amount of financial resources required for investment projects, which are summarized in a recommendation to the relevant stakeholders (i.e. owner, bank, government) and provide an advantage to facilitate monitoring and control related to the company's objectives [14]. In practice, an FS report is prepared by the investor and submitted to the contracting authority to audit its contents, study the possibility of the investor recovering his disbursements, and achieve a reasonable return, in addition to studying the project's potential to add social, environmental, and economic benefits.

A. Types of Feasibility Studies

There are two main FS types:

- A preliminary FS follows the project's first value proposition, providing a general overview using multiple analytical frameworks that allow the expert to recommend its applicability [15]. A legal FS is carried out to examine whether the proposed plan or system complies with national or international legal regulations [16]. Protection acts serve as a means to determine law violations [17].
- A detailed FS includes a set of studies (social, technical, market, financial, environmental, and economic), in which data and information necessary to evaluate investment projects are collected, studied, examined, and evaluated to determine the feasibility of investing in them, and the extent to which they can succeed and grow, and then put them into practice [18-20].

B. Necessities and Non-Necessities of Feasibility Studies

An FS is necessary for all projects [21]. However, certain projects are implemented without the need for an FS. Table I illustrates the types of projects that require the execution of an FS, as well as the types where FS is typically not executed.

C. Who Prepares the Feasibility Study?

Contracting authorities prepare themselves the FSs or hire external consultants [22-23]. If external consultants are hired, the authority staff is involved in the complete study development process and provides most of the information and data required to assess the situation, including costs, staffing, etc. Hiring a consultant to prepare the FS is an important decision for contracting authorities and line ministries. Contracting authorities must take care and select a technically proficient consultant to undertake it, considering the following selection criteria:

- Experience in conducting feasibility studies
- Strong background in both financial and technical aspects of different types of projects
- Experience in the industry being studied

- Working independently and objectively
- Fair and neutral decision making
- Experience in data collection and manipulation
- Working closely with the designated MOP and line ministries team
- Working with the assigned budget
- Strong presentation and communication skills

TABLE I. TYPES OF PROJECTS THAT NEED FS

Category	Example	Remarks
An FS is necessary	Infrastructure project involving an extensive development plan	Economic zones, power plants, ports, toll roads, large bridge
	Improvement project with extension or broadening plan and possible social influences	Example: expansion of an existing hospital from 50 to 250 beds
	Commercial project: e.g. toll road, touristic project	Financial analysis will be prioritized
FS is usually not necessary	Immediate measures to mitigate the impact of natural disasters	The countermeasure project aims to mitigate the impact of disasters by adopting a long-term view. It is a focal point for FS
	Symbolic/religious project	e.g. Parliament Halls, National Universities, public parks, sports stadiums, national cemeteries, National Mosques, etc.
	Expansion/maintenance project with normal demand	FS may be needed for peculiar situations, e.g. when there will be a lot of traffic during a road project
	Small project	Internally evaluated based on the project concept
	A project devoiding of any potential for feasibility	As a consequence of the evaluation conducted by the project concept
	Study/survey project on how to find solutions to current issues	It will be looked at by a project concept or a basic study, for example, to see if it will have any environmental effects

D. Feasibility Study Process

Every detailed FS has a rigorous process to follow [24]. If a large project needs a detailed FS, then a pre-FS should indicate a Go/No-Go signal. Figure 1 shows the process that is maintained for project development.

Fig. 1. Feasibility study process.

III. CASE STUDY

Landfilling is the only method used in Iraq to treat solid waste. Several studies have shown that treating solid waste using the landfilling method can have many negative impacts, including high financial costs, soil and groundwater pollution, and the emission of toxic substances and gases such as methane. One of the best solutions for treating solid waste is to use it for energy production (Waste to Energy, W2E). This process requires the establishment of a Feed-In-Tariff (FIT).

A. FIT to W2E

In deciding the FIT for W2E, one needs to consider the following cost and financing elements. The example here is a project that would take care of 2,250 tons/day of Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) and turn it into electrical energy.

1) Investment Cost

The investment for a plant that would handle 2,250 tons/day of MSW, which could have a generation capacity of 50 MW at minimum, would cost the order of \$350,000,000. This would be financed through banks, private financiers, or financial institutions at a rate that reflects the risk appetite of those who would like to lend their money to Iraq for this project. The perceived risk and the related ranking of that country mostly shape the risk appetite. At this risk level, borrowing funds from Iraq would be costly. The only upside is that this is an environmentally friendly project that would eliminate the emission of hazardous gases into the environment, where given the global environment, the Paris Agenda, and the 2050 targets, locating funds at somewhat lower rates might still be possible. The level of risk in Iraq and the size of the project would require government support, either in the form of a Treasury Guarantee or a Bank Letter of Guarantee (BLG) from the Trade Bank of Iraq (TBI) and endorsed by a first-class international bank. The interest rate to finance this project could be 7.5% per year.

2) Political Risk Insurance (PRI)

PRI covers non-commercial risks, political events, and direct or indirect government actions that could affect investment returns [25]. Although there are various forms of PRI, not all PRI providers would provide or offer cover for all the risks, but depending on the risk rating of the country, they would offer cover for some of the following risks: expropriation, transfer restrictions, currency inconvertibility, political violence, contract default, war, and civil unrest, etc. Although this is rather a very costly insurance, on the other hand, it becomes an enabler for establishing the required financing. PRI could be obtained from international private insurance companies or bilateral agencies, depending on the supply of equipment from these countries, or multilateral agencies such as MIGA, World Bank, or Asian Development

Bank (ADB). The rates change over the years, depending on the changes in the country and the availability of PRI in the market. Therefore, the PRI cost is estimated to be more than 2% per year.

3) Operation and Maintenance (O&M) Costs

Yearly O&M costs, including staff, were projected at \$15 million.

4) Renewal Costs

O&M cost does not cover the long-term maintenance and replacement cost for equipment. The equipment would require a major overhaul in certain periods, depending on the equipment and its working condition, which could range from 3 to 10 years. Some equipment would even require total replacement. Renewal costs were proposed to be 1% per year.

5) Cost of Fuel and Water

MSW is the fuel for the plant. Both MSW and water should be supplied free of charge to the plant.

6) Land

The land should be available for free during the project terms for 25 years, under a lease contract. This should be on the order of 200,000 m².

B. Amount of MSW and Calorific Value

The depletion of fossil fuel reserves has tempted research and development programs to compensate for the deficit by switching to alternative energy sources [26]. MSW is the fuel for this W2E plant, and the calculations are based on the waste composition provided by the Baghdad Municipalities, as given in Table II. This composition is expected to have a Calorific Value (CV) of 7.5 MJ/Kg. Table III shows the average ratios of secretion components per person for the Baghdad province. The values in Table II represent the most important parameters in the project calculations. A higher portion of plastics, cardboard, etc., has a higher CV [27]. Therefore, it will produce more heat, which in turn will generate more electricity. However, more watery or organic content will have less CV, resulting in less electricity. The general rule of recommendation is that if the CV is less than 6.0 MJ/kg, then incineration should not be used to eliminate MSW. The MSW should be supplied free of charge by the municipality, and daily average quantities should be guaranteed. The calorific value is most important for the amount of power to be produced. A mechanism should be established to ensure CV. The CV of the MSW must be studied, and the municipality has to guarantee not only the amount but also its CV value. Otherwise, it would be like giving less fuel to a car and expecting the car to travel the same mileage with much less fuel.

TABLE II. SOLID WASTE COMPONENTS AND CV

Components	Organic	Plastics	Paper	Glass	Metal	Other	Total
Tons per Year	363814	127294	121545	66521	63236	78840	821250
%	44.3	15.5	14.8	8.1	7.7	9.6	100
MJ/kg	5.2	22.5	11.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	Avg. 7.5
Energy (MJ)	1.89×10 ⁹	2.88×10 ⁹	1.42×10 ⁹	0	0	0	6.19×10 ⁹

TABLE III. AVERAGE RATIO OF SECRETION COMPONENTS PER PERSON FOR BAGHDAD PROVINCE

Year	Organic	Plastics	Paper	Metal	Glass	Other	Total
2017	46.4	15.5	14.6	8.2	7.8	7.5	100
2018	45.18	16.1	14.81	7.27	8.01	8.63	100
2019	43.19	20.93	17.68	6.8	6.25	5.15	100
2020	43.4	19.6	21.7	5.7	4.5	5.1	100
2021	42.25	20.5	21.75	5.5	5.5	4.5	100
Avg. (%)	44.08	18.53	18.11	6.69	6.41	6.18	100

C. Remuneration of the Investment (Take or Pay)

With the above investment, the investor can handle 2,250 tons/day of MSW. The investor should ensure that the facility performs at its optimal performance throughout the project. The buyer should ensure that the facility is properly fed daily with the required fuel. According to the contract, the investor would require the buyer to provide the MSW at a CV of not less than 7.5 MJ/Kg. Higher content of plastics and paper, etc., would provide more heat and therefore more electricity, whereas providing more organic would mean less CV and therefore less power. The investor would design the plant capacity at the pre-agreed level of CV and tonnage of MSW. When the plant is commissioned, tests will be run to confirm its electricity production capacity. This capacity would then be adjusted for the CV of the MSW supplied, setting the reliable capacity for the plant. With the contract, the buyer would commit to buying all the power produced from the plant and paying for it at FIT prices. However, if the plant cannot produce, for example, if not enough MSW is supplied or any other similar reason that is beyond the investor's control, the buyer then also commits to pay the full dependable capacity, whether it is produced or not. In other words, it is a Take-or-Pay for capacity.

D. Production Capacity and Return

This plant is estimated to produce 430 TWh of electricity per year with 91% availability. A higher CV of MSW could result in a higher level of electricity generation. Initially, all the income from payments would be given back to the lenders. There would be a significant interest cost during this period until the borrowed sums are returned. Therefore, there must be a higher level of FIT during this period to ensure that financial institutions receive their returns. Subsequently, the rates could be significantly reduced. In this case, the investor should state that the rates should not be less than \$0.19/kWh for the first seven years and then \$0.10/kWh for the remaining 18 years to provide an acceptable Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and Return on Investment (ROI).

E. Benefits of the Project

The benefits of this project can be identified as:

- A better and healthier environment through the elimination of waste: This plant eliminates the total organic content of the MSW. Without building this plant, the municipality must eliminate MSW using landfills with appropriate impermeable membrane ground cover, etc. Although the plant would generate electricity, it requires some investment. However, what is more important is that landfills need careful handling of both gaseous emissions and groundwater contamination issues. The odors of

decaying matter become a concern for the public living nearby.

- Reduction in Green House Gases (GHG): As mentioned above, dealing with MSW will reduce hazardous gases that are of great concern globally and contribute to global warming. This would be achieved in two ways: elimination of methane gas emissions from landfills and electricity generated would replace electricity that would otherwise be generated from fossil-based fuels. The project would significantly contribute to Iraq's commitment to the Paris Agenda of eliminating hazardous gases and limiting global warming by 2050.
- Job creation: The plant is expected to employ 74 people, electrical or mechanical technicians, various plant personnel, security, etc. The cost of salaries and benefits would be \$1.5 million. Job creation is one of the key elements for investment worldwide, in developed or developing countries. The high unemployment rate is always a social concern and will remain so, and employment provides value to the economy.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

FSs are considered the basis for the rest of investment project studies. These studies provide the investor and the project owner with information related to the technical, environmental, social, financial, and economic aspects of the project. Consequently, government institutions sponsoring investment projects must emphasize that investors should pay special attention to this type of study due to its importance in uncovering feasible projects. FSs are required for all types of projects, but in some cases, they are not necessary, such as in projects related to urgent countermeasures after natural disasters.

FSs must be prepared by experts who have sufficient experience in all technical, financial, and economic aspects, and the environmental aspect of the study should be prepared separately by an expert on environmental issues. For the W2E project shown above, although difficult to quantify in monetary terms, the W2E plant delivers an alternative to landfills without concern for odors, land, and air pollution. Such projects have greater social revenues than the economic revenues sought by most investors. Therefore, the government must support investment in such projects and provide all requirements and privileges to investors. Waste energy has been proven to be a clean, environmentally friendly, and effective source of electricity throughout the world. The safest and most economically viable way to deal with MSW is to convert it into energy.

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Advanced Fraud Detection in Blockchain Transactions: An Ensemble Learning and Explainable AI Approach

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, cryptocurrencies have experienced rapid growth and adoption, revolutionizing the financial sector. However, the rise of digital currencies has also led to an increase in fraudulent transactions and illegal activities. In this paper, we present a comprehensive study on the detection of fraudulent transactions in the context of cryptocurrency exchanges, with a primary focus on the Ethereum network. By employing various Machine Learning (ML) techniques and ensemble methods, including the hard voting ensemble model, which achieved a remarkable 99% accuracy, we aim to effectively identify suspicious transactions while maintaining high accuracy and precision. Additionally, we delve into the importance of eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to enhance transparency, trust, and accountability in AI-based fraud detection systems. Our research contributes to the development of reliable and interpretable models that can significantly improve the cryptocurrency ecosystem security and integrity.

Keywords-blockchain; Ethereum; fraudulent transactions; machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of cryptocurrencies and the adoption of blockchain (BC) technology have revolutionized the financial sector, offering new opportunities for investment and secure online transactions [1]. BC, an advanced and rapidly evolving technology, offers a more secure alternative by providing a distributed, decentralized, and immutable ledger for recording transactions [2]. Despite the advantages of decentralized systems, cryptocurrencies face significant challenges in detecting and preventing fraudulent transactions [3]. These illicit activities not only harm the economy but also erode public trust in BC-based solutions. BC networks aim to detect and mitigate fraudulent transactions as quickly as possible to maintain community integrity and security [4]. The anonymous nature of BC transactions and the decentralized nature of cryptocurrencies make fraud detection a complex and challenging task [5]. The rise of digital currencies has led to an increase in financial transactions conducted online [6], with traditional currencies being converted into their digital

counterparts. Although this modernization offers convenience and efficiency, it also exposes transactions to potential security breaches, such as fraud, anomalies, and privacy violations. As the volume of transactions increases, so does the risk of fraudulent activities, resulting in significant financial losses. Even within BC networks, malicious actors can exploit vulnerabilities and engage in fraudulent activities [7, 8]. Therefore, it is crucial to develop and implement robust techniques to detect and prevent fraudulent transactions in cryptocurrencies. This paper aims to explore and evaluate ML models for Ethereum Fraud Detection (EFD), focusing on ensemble learning and XAI to improve system accuracy and transparency. By addressing these challenges, we hope to contribute to the development of more secure and trustworthy BC-based financial solutions.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Blockchain and Decentralized Applications

At its core, BC is a manifestation of Distributed Ledger

Technology (DLT) [9]. This revolutionary technology facilitates consensus and validation of transactions across a computer network, thereby eliminating the need for a central or intermediary authority [10]. Each validated transaction, along with others, forms a new "block" that is added to an existing chain of transactions, giving rise to the term Blockchain [11, 12]. BC networks are typically categorized into permissioned and permissionless BCs. Permissioned BCs are exclusive networks utilized by specific individuals or entities, such as a consortium of banks conducting financial transactions [13]. On the other hand, permissionless or public BCs, like the Bitcoin network where transactions are conducted using Bitcoin as an exchange medium, are open source networks accessible to anyone [14]. A key feature of these networks is the use of smart contracts. These are self-executing contracts with the agreement terms directly written into code. Smart contracts automate and secure transactions, making them an integral part of decentralized applications (dApps). dApps are applications that run on a peer to peer computer network, leveraging BC technology principles to create secure, transparent, and resistant to censorship systems [9]. BC operates as a decentralized peer to peer network, where control over the data is not concentrated in any single node or group of nodes [15]. Instead, all nodes connected to the BC network share equal authority over the latter. Immutability is a defining characteristic of BC, safeguarding against data alteration [16]. BC maintains an append-only digital ledger, meaning that once data are added to the network, they cannot be edited or deleted. Every connected node in a BC network has a copy of the current ledger [11], making the data within the specific network accessible to all connected participants and ensuring system transparency and availability. The foundational understanding of BC technology, along with the use of smart contracts, paves the way for the development and application of dApps. These applications have a wide range of uses, from decentralized finance (DeFi) [17] where they provide financial services in a more open, accessible, and equitable manner. They are also used in voting systems [18], enhancing the voting process transparency and security. Furthermore, dApps are utilized in supply chain management, where they provide real-time, transparent tracking of goods, enhancing efficiency and accountability [19]. They are also making inroads into the gaming industry, creating decentralized gaming platforms that offer true ownership of game assets [20]. In the content management field, dApps enable creators to publish and monetize their content without the need for intermediaries [21].

B. Ethereum

Ethereum is a decentralized, open-source BC platform known for its smart contract functionality [20]. It was proposed in 2013 by programmer Vitalik Buterin and its development was crowdfunded in 2014, with the network going live on July 30, 2015 [22]. In contrast to Bitcoin, which is primarily a digital currency, Ethereum's primary goal is to serve as a platform for decentralized applications (dApps). These dApps are designed to operate without any downtime, fraud, control, or interference from a third party. Ethereum's platform specific cryptographic token, Ether, is the fuel that powers these applications [44]. Ether serves two main functions: it acts as a digital currency exchange similar to Bitcoin, and it is used

within the Ethereum platform to run applications and even monetize work. A significant innovation of Ethereum is the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM), a Turing complete software that operates on the Ethereum network. The EVM allows any program to be run, regardless of the programming language, as long as sufficient time and memory are provided. The EVM streamlines the creation of multiple diverse BC applications on a single platform [45]. As other cryptocurrencies, Ethereum functions on a decentralized network, which makes it a compelling platform for implementing smart contracts and developing decentralized applications (dApps). However, this decentralization also opens up avenues for fraudulent activities. For instance, Ethereum is susceptible to a 51% attack, where if a miner or a group of miners possesses more than half of the network's computing capability, they can rewrite the BC, leading to potential fraud [23]

C. Explainable AI (XAI)

XAI is a research area that aims to design algorithms and methods which allow AI models to offer clear and human understandable explanations for their predictions and decisions [24]. The primary objective of Interpretable AI is to improve transparency, accountability, and trust in AI systems by helping humans comprehend the rationale behind model outcomes [25]. Within the realm of cybersecurity, Interpretable AI plays a crucial role in detecting and mitigating cyber threats [26]. AI models are utilized by cybersecurity professionals to analyze vast quantities of data and pinpoint potential threats. However, due to the opaque nature of these models, understanding their decision-making process can be challenging, leaving experts uncertain about the appropriate response to identified threats [27]. By incorporating Interpretable AI, cybersecurity specialists can gain a better understanding of the AI model's predictions, which allows them to make well informed decisions when addressing cyber threats [25].

Locally Interpretable Model Agnostic Explanations(LIME) is designed to create an intelligible model that utilizes an easily understandable representation while preserving local fidelity to the original classifier[28]. Given an instance with its original representation, $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and an explanation model, $g \in G$, where G represents a set of visually expressible, interpretable models (e.g. a linear model), the explanation provided by LIME can be formulated as follows:

$$\phi(x) = \arg \min L[(f, g, \omega x) + \Omega(g)] \quad (1)$$

In (1), f symbolizes the classification model, ωx denotes a similarity measure between the original and new instances (with higher values indicating greater similarity), L is the loss function that assesses the proximity of the predictions between the explanation and original models, and $\Omega(g)$ quantifies the complexity of model g . LIME strives to develop a model that is both locally focused and interpretable. To accomplish this, LIME minimizes the function $L[(f, g, \omega x) + \Omega(g)]$, where f is the original model, g is the locally derived interpretation model, and ωx is a weight vector for instance x . The regularization term $\Omega(g)$ assists in preventing overfitting of the interpretation model. Upon minimizing the objective function, LIME generates an explanation for a specific instance using the locally derived interpretation model $\phi(x)$. The interpretation

model $\phi(x)$ is intended to be straightforward and transparent, which makes it more accessible for humans to grasp the reasoning behind a particular prediction. By employing a locally focused and interpretable model, LIME offers insights into the decision making processes of complex models.

D. Ensemble Techniques

Ensemble techniques combine the predictions of multiple base models to improve the performance and accuracy of the final predictions [29]. In this study, we employed two widely used ensemble methods: Hard Voting and Soft Voting. Both methods utilize the outputs of multiple classifiers to produce a more robust and accurate final decision.

- **Majority Voting:** Majority Voting, also known as Hard Voting, is a straightforward ensemble method that considers the class labels predicted by individual base models. For each input, the class label that receives the majority of votes from the base models is chosen as the final prediction [30]. This approach is particularly effective when the base models have complementary strengths and weaknesses, as it enables the ensemble to collectively capitalize on their individual advantages.
- **Probabilistic Voting:** Probabilistic Voting, or Soft Voting, is a more sophisticated ensemble technique that takes into account the predicted class probabilities generated by the base models [31]. Instead of simply counting the votes for each class label, Soft Voting computes the average of the predicted probabilities for each class and selects the class with the highest average probability as the final prediction [32]. This method can yield better performance than Hard Voting, especially when the base models provide well calibrated probability estimates.

III. ETHEREUM FRAUD DETECTION USING MACHINE LEARNING

BC technologies are being implemented across various public and private sectors due to their ability to secure and monitor auditing systems effectively [14]. These technologies facilitate the evaluation of data repositories, allowing auditors to submit queries in a secure and user-friendly manner without disclosing their identities to unauthorized parties [33]. In [34], consensus algorithms are utilized to confirm the validity of conducted transactions; however, they fall short in accurately identifying transactions. Consequently, solely depending on BC for fraud detection is not a comprehensive solution. To tackle this issue, alternative strategies, such as the application of ML algorithms, are explored to eliminate existing system vulnerabilities. Multiple supervised ML techniques are deployed to detect fraudulent transactions, and an extensive comparison of these approaches is conducted. KaRuNa [35] is a decentralized framework that leverages BC technology for sentiment analysis to detect fraudulent cryptocurrency schemes. Operating on a public BC, KaRuNa is composed of three trust modeling phases involving stakeholders. The initial phase includes transaction execution on the BC, which fosters trust, auditability, and transparency among participants. The subsequent phase proposes a sentiment analysis of cryptocurrencies, employing a unique hashing algorithm for addresses to produce classification scores. This phase takes into

account various factors such as social trends, cryptocurrency price volatility, calculated standard deviation, and peak and trough values. These factors are integrated into a novel Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) classifier to generate recommendations. Impressively, the LSTM classifier demonstrates an accuracy of 98.99% in evaluating investment risks based on the generated classification scores.

By analyzing 2,179 accounts flagged for illicit activity and 2,502 normal accounts within the Ethereum community, authors in [3] aim to detect malicious accounts based on their transaction history using the XGBoost classifier. Through 10-fold cross-validation, XGBoost achieved an average accuracy of 0.963 (± 0.006) and an average AUC of 0.994 (± 0.0007). The most influential features for the final model were identified as "Time diff between first and last (μ ins)," "Total Ether balance," and "Min value received." Authors in [36] explore the application of various supervised ML approaches to identify and differentiate between fraudulent and legitimate transactions. An in depth comparative analysis of several supervised ML algorithms is conducted for this purpose. It was found that the most effective results (accuracy: 97%) were achieved using Ada Boost, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest (RF) classifiers, outperforming the other seven algorithms examined. In [37], the researchers focused on extracting more comprehensive features from Bitcoin transaction data to improve the detection of fraudulent activities. To address the issue of imbalanced data, measures were taken to equalize the dataset. Several supervised methods, including KNN, SVM, RF, AdaBoost, and MLP, were employed. Additionally, three unsupervised methods, namely the One Class SVM (OCSVM), Local Outlier Factor (LOF), and Mahalanobis Distance Based (MDB) approach, were utilized for detection purposes. The best performing algorithm among these approaches was the RF, exhibiting impressive recall, precision, and F1 scores of 95.9%. These findings demonstrate the efficacy of the RF algorithm in accurately identifying fraudulent activities in Bitcoin transactions. In a related study [33], supervised methods including RF, SVM, and XGBoost were employed to detect fraudulent accounts in the Ethereum BC. The study successfully achieved high recall and precision values, which enabled the design of an effective antifraud rule for digital wallets or currency exchanges. This study introduces a novel detection mechanism called Ethereum Phishing Scam Detection (Eth-PSD) aimed at identifying phishing scam related transactions using an ML based approach [38]. Eth-PSD addresses various limitations present in existing works, including imbalanced datasets, complex feature engineering, and lower detection accuracy. Additionally, an investigation was conducted into constructing a new, updated, and balanced dataset specifically designed for effectively evaluating Eth-PSD performance. The experimental results demonstrate that Eth-PSD exhibits high efficiency in detecting phishing scams on the Ethereum platform, achieving a remarkable detection accuracy of 98.11% while maintaining a very low False Positive Rate of 0.01. By mitigating the shortcomings of previous approaches, Eth-PSD presents a promising solution for combating phishing scams in the Ethereum ecosystem. Authors in [40] present an innovative approach that leverages the integration of ML techniques and

BC technology to combat fraud in the healthcare sector, specifically in claims processing. The proposed methodology revolves around the utilization of a decision tree classification algorithm to accurately categorize the original claims dataset. Subsequently, the acquired knowledge is translated into a smart contract deployed on the Ethereum BC, facilitating the detection and prevention of healthcare fraud. Through meticulous comparative experiments, the results underscore the remarkable performance of the proposed system, achieving an impressive classification accuracy of 97.96% and an exceptional sensitivity of 98.09%. These outcomes highlight the profound impact of the BC smart contract in fortifying fraud detection capabilities, leading to an unparalleled accuracy rate of 97.96%. Authors in [40] introduce ContractWard, an original approach aimed at identifying vulnerabilities in smart contracts through the utilization of machine learning techniques. By leveraging bigram features extracted from simplified operation codes of smart contracts, ContractWard constructs robust detection models using a combination of five distinct ML algorithms and two sampling algorithms. Notably, the evaluation conducted on a comprehensive dataset of real-world smart contracts deployed on Ethereum showcases ContractWard's exceptional performance, achieving remarkably high predictive scores of over 96% for both Micro-F1 and Macro-F1 metrics. Moreover, ContractWard demonstrates impressive efficiency, with an average detection time of 4 s per smart contract when trained with XGBoost whereas it was balanced with the SMOTE Tomek. These findings unequivocally underscore the efficacy and proficiency of ContractWard in effectively identifying vulnerabilities and fortifying the security of smart contracts.

IV. PROPOSED SCHEME

In our methodology (Figure 1), we will begin by collecting the EFD dataset. This dataset will undergo preprocessing to prepare the data for analysis. Following that, we will use three different algorithms for making predictions: Random Forest (RF), AdaBoost, and Decision Tree (DT). Each of these algorithms will produce its own prediction (Pred1, Pred2, and Pred3, respectively). Once the predictions are made, we will apply Hard Voting and Soft Voting, leading to two sets of predictions (Pred_H and Pred_S). The predictions will then be evaluated to assess the performance of our ensemble method. As part of the evaluation, we will also employ techniques from XAI to interpret the results and provide insights into how the decisions were made by the ensemble.

A. Dataset

The dataset [41] we used in our study provides a comprehensive view of Ethereum transactions, with a specific focus on identifying fraudulent activities. It encompasses various attributes ranging from basic account information to more detailed transactional data. Each record in the dataset represents an Ethereum account and includes the unique account address and a flag indicating whether transactions from the account are fraudulent. Transaction timings are dissected into average minutes between transactions, both sent and received, as well as the time difference between the first and last transaction, illustrating account activity over time.

The dataset quantifies the number of transactions sent and received, including the creation of contract transactions, which are crucial for understanding account behavior. It also delves into the uniqueness of interaction by accounting for the total unique addresses involved in both incoming and outgoing transactions. The transactional values are broken down into minimum, maximum, and average Ether values sent and received, providing a financial profile of each account's activity. This extends to transactions involving contracts, with separate metrics for Ether sent to contracts, thus highlighting the role of smart contracts in the transactional ecosystem of an account.

Fig. 1. The proposed methodology.

Moreover, the dataset provides a holistic view of an account's Ether flow, summarizing total transactions, total Ethers sent and received, and the overall balance of Ether post-transactions. It paints a detailed picture of an account's engagement with ERC20 token transactions, including the total number of these transactions, the Ether value of ERC20 tokens sent and received, and interactions with contract addresses specifically for ERC20 tokens. The dataset does not just stop at quantity but also explores the diversity of tokens associated with the accounts, listing the number of unique ERC20 tokens sent and received, as well as the most frequently sent and received token types. This rich dataset serves as the backbone of our analysis, providing us with the necessary depth and breadth of data to accurately model and detect fraudulent transactions in the Ethereum network.

B. Data Pre-processing

Data preprocessing stands as a pivotal phase in the deployment of ML methodologies, aiming to enhance model accuracy and accelerate the learning process. This stage is critical for the elimination of non-contributing attributes, the

resolution of missing values, and the rectification of imbalances within the dataset, which are essential to optimize the predictive prowess of the algorithms employed. In the realm of data cleansing, we judiciously excised three variables from our dataset deemed non-essential for the task of EFD. These excluded features—specifically the "Address," "ERC20 most sent token type," and "ERC20 most received token type" were identified as extraneous in the context of our analytical objectives, thereby streamlining the feature space to those of greater pertinence[43]. Addressing the prevalence of incomplete records, we invoked the capabilities of the datasets library, a Python toolkit tailored for facile data operations and exploration. We engaged the "fill missing num" functionality to impute voids within numerical attributes, substituting absent values with the feature's mean. Concurrently, the "fill missing cats" mechanism was employed to rectify gaps in categorical features, defaulting missing entries to the mode of the respective attribute.

Given the inherent challenge posed by skewed class distributions, our dataset's imbalance was manifest, with a scant proportion of fraudulent transactions (2,179 out of 9,841). To mitigate the bias towards the predominant class and enhance the model sensitivity to the minority class, we implemented two resampling strategies: Random Under Sampling (RUS) and Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE). These techniques are instrumental in recalibrating the dataset to a more balanced composition, thereby facilitating a more equitable and nuanced learning process.

C. Model Implementation

In our ensemble framework, we methodically implemented three machine learning models: RF, DT, and AdaBoost, each chosen for its distinct characteristics and ability to uncover patterns of fraudulent activity in the Ethereum dataset.

The RF model, known for its proficiency in managing datasets with numerous features, was applied by constructing a series of DTs, each on different data and feature subsets. This ensemble approach reduces overfitting risks inherent in single DTs by averaging out biases and errors, which results in improved prediction accuracy. We tailored the RF hyperparameters, such as the number of trees and the maximum depth of the trees, to suit the complexity of our data.

In the case of the DT model, we capitalized on its straightforward structure to build a model that splits the data based on certain feature thresholds. These splits were carefully chosen to maximize the differentiation between fraudulent and non-fraudulent transactions. The simplicity of a single DT allows for easy interpretation of decision paths but requires careful monitoring to prevent overfitting to the training data.

The AdaBoost algorithm was chosen for its adaptive qualities, boosting the classification capabilities of weak learners, typically DTs in our case. AdaBoost focuses on instances that have been challenging for previous models, iteratively adjusting the weights of these instances. By doing so, subsequent models prioritize these difficult cases in the training process. The final model is then a composite of these individual learners, weighted by their accuracy, to form a

robust classifier. For AdaBoost, we selected an appropriate number of DTs to serve as weak learners, ensuring they collectively form a strong predictive model without overcomplicating the learning process.

For each model, we meticulously adjusted their respective hyperparameters, such as the number of estimators for RF and AdaBoost and the depth for DT, according to the specific demands of our dataset. This fine-tuning was essential to balance the bias-variance tradeoff, aiming to maximize the predictive performance while maintaining the models' abilities to generalize new data. The individual strengths of RF, DT, and AdaBoost, when integrated within our ensemble strategy, resulted in a comprehensive and robust fraud detection mechanism.

D. Ensemble Learning

Ensemble learning in the context of our fraud detection system is the strategic combination of multiple machine learning models to improve the overall predictive performance. This approach leverages the strengths of individual models to create a collective decision-making entity that is more accurate and reliable than any single model alone. The ensemble technique is particularly effective in complex problems like fraud detection, where the nuances of fraudulent behavior can be difficult for a single model to capture.

Our ensemble consists of three well-established algorithms, RF, DT, and AdaBoost. The RF model contributes its ensemble of DTs that individually assess different aspects of the data, thus offering a comprehensive view through majority voting. The strength of this model lies in its ability to mitigate the overfitting problem commonly seen in individual DTs by averaging multiple decision paths. The DT model brings clarity and interpretability to the ensemble. It offers a depth of analysis at each decision node, which is valuable for understanding the specific conditions that lead to a classification of fraud. The tree's structure provides clear rules and criteria for decision-making, which can be crucial for stakeholders requiring insight into the model's reasoning. AdaBoost complements the ensemble by focusing on instances that are difficult to classify. It operates by sequentially applying weak learners and adjusting their focus on misclassified instances from the previous models. The learning algorithm adapts by giving more weight to the misjudged instances, ensuring that subsequent learners give them more attention. The resulting combination of these learners forms a potent model that can handle varied and complex fraud patterns.

In our ensemble, each model votes on the outcome of a transaction being fraudulent or not, with the final decision achieved through aggregation methods, like hard voting or soft voting. Hard voting considers the most common outcome predicted by the models, while soft voting takes into account the confidence level of each prediction. This harmonization of diverse models and voting mechanisms ensures that the ensemble captures an expansive spectrum of data patterns and anomalies, leading to a robust and nuanced fraud detection system. By integrating these models' predictions, we aim to harness their collective intelligence, thereby enhancing the

accuracy and reliability of detecting fraud within the Ethereum network.

V. MODEL TRAINING AND EVALUATION

The dataset was divided into two portions: one for training and evaluation, accounting for 80% of the data, and the other for testing with unseen data, comprising the remaining 20%. For our experiments, we employed Google Colab, a collaborative Jupyter notebook platform, to conduct our ML research. We utilized Keras (version 2.12.0) and TensorFlow (version 2.12.0), as a backend engine. Our experimental setup in the Google Colab environment provided us with 13.62 GB of available RAM, offering a powerful and accessible resource for implementing and testing our models. The primary objective of our study was to design and evaluate ML models using the EFD dataset to categorize Ethereum transactions into two groups: legitimate and fraudulent. The "Flag" feature served as the target variable for training and evaluation. We assessed the performance of various ML methods by measuring metrics such as accuracy, training time, recall, precision, and F-score.

The performance results for the three individual ML classifiers and two ensemble voting strategies used in EFD can be seen in Table I. The RF classifier showcases the highest accuracy of 98.7%, with a precision, recall, and F1 score of 0.99 for both fraudulent and legitimate labels. It, however, requires a considerable training time of 3.35 s. The DT classifier exhibits an accuracy of 97.3%, with corresponding precision, recall, and F1 scores of 0.97. Despite its slightly lower accuracy, it has the benefit of a relatively shorter training time of just 0.2 s. The AdaBoost classifier aligns closely with the DT classifier, with accuracy of 97.6% and similar precision, recall, and F1 scores, but at a longer training time of 2.32 s. When we consider the ensemble methods, both soft and hard voting mechanisms show promising results. The Soft Voting method achieves an accuracy of 98%, albeit with the longest training time of 4.59 s. The Hard Voting method, in contrast, achieves the highest accuracy of 99%, surpassing all individual classifiers and the Soft Voting method, while requiring a moderate training time of 3.85 s.

TABLE I. ETHEREUM FRAUD DETECTION RESULTS

Classifier	ACC	Training Time (s)	Label	PREC	REC	F-S
RF	98.7%	3.35	Fraudulent	0.99	0.99	0.99
			Legitimate	0.99	0.99	0.99
DT	97.3%	0.2	Fraudulent	0.97	0.97	0.97
			Legitimate	0.97	0.97	0.97
AdaBoost	97.6%	2.32	Fraudulent	0.98	0.97	0.98

Based on these outcomes, the Ensemble Hard Voting classifier emerges as the most effective model for EFD due to its highest accuracy of 99%. Although its training time is not the shortest, the superior accuracy compensates for the extra computational resources, given the critical nature of fraud detection in BC transactions.

The results underscore the importance of ensemble methods in enhancing the robustness and accuracy of fraud detection

models, thus contributing significantly to the security aspect of BC technologies.

The comparative evaluation of our proposed Ensemble Hard Voting classifier against other methods presented in the existing literature further underscores its superior performance (Table II). With an ACC of 99%, the proposed model surpasses the accuracies reported in [3, 36, 38, 39, 42]. Not only does this comparison illustrate the efficiency of the proposed model, but also demonstrates its contribution to the ongoing research in EFD. The incorporation of ensemble methods and specifically the Hard Voting classifier enhances the robustness and accuracy of the detection system, thereby strengthening the security framework of BC transactions. These findings emphasize the growing potential of ML-driven solutions in managing the intricate cybersecurity challenges within the constantly evolving BC sphere.

TABLE II. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EFD ACCURACY: PROPOSED VS. EXISTING METHODS

Reference	ACC
Proposed	99%
[3]	96.3%
[36]	98%
[42]	80.2%
[38]	98.11%
[39]	97.96%

The significance of explainability in AI cannot be overstated, particularly when it pertains to high-stake domains, such as fraud detection. A fundamental step towards achieving transparency in AI models is the examination of feature importance, which sheds light on the variables that most significantly influence the model's predictions.

In our analysis (Figure 2), the RF classifier has highlighted the differential impact of various features. The prominence of "Time diff between first and last (mins)" at the apex of importance underscores its pivotal role in identifying potential fraud. Such insights are invaluable, as not only do they inform the model's predictive behavior, but also provide stakeholders with an understanding of the underlying factors that the AI considers indicative of fraudulent activities. The feature importance graph also accentuates the relevance of ERC20 token transactions, with features such as "ERC20 min val rec," "ERC20 max val rec," and "ERC20 avg val rec" ranking highly. The significance attributed to these features reveals the model's sensitivity to the nuances of smart contract interactions on the Ethereum platform. By delineating the hierarchy of feature importance, XAI demystifies the model's decision-making process, enabling a more informed and transparent evaluation of the model's outputs. Not only does this approach ensure that the most impactful features are incorporated into the model, enhancing its accuracy, but also fosters trust and credibility in the AI system by making its inner workings more accessible to users and practitioners.

The LIME technique stands as a pivotal tool in the realm of explainable AI, providing clarity on how predictive models make their decisions. It achieves this by generating local surrogate models that approximate the predictions of the complex model in a comprehensible way. The bar chart

produced by LIME offers an intuitive visualization of the importance of individual features for a particular prediction. In the context of our fraud detection model, LIME elucidates the contributions of specific features to the classification of a transaction (Figure 3). For instance, the "Unique received from addresses" feature has a significant positive impact on classifying a transaction as class 1, which could represent a

fraudulent transaction. Similarly, "ERC20 min val sent" and "ERC20 total Ether sent contract" are also influential in the model's prediction, as depicted by their weight in the chart. The negative weight of "Time diff between first and last (mins)" suggests that shorter time differences may decrease the likelihood of a transaction being classified as class 1.

Fig. 2. Feature importance rankings utilizing the RF classifier.

Fig. 3. Feature importance rankings utilizing the LIME technique.

LIME's granular explanations offer valuable insights, particularly in scenarios where model trustworthiness and understanding are critical. By dissecting the model's predictions into interpretable contributions from each feature,

stakeholders can gain a nuanced understanding of the model's behavior, which is instrumental for validation and trust in AI applications.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study has underscored the power of ML techniques, notably the Hard Voting ensemble model, in detecting fraudulent transactions within the complex world of cryptocurrencies. The research has illuminated the capability of these methodologies in identifying questionable activities, while simultaneously underscoring the value of Explainable AI (XAI) in ensuring transparency, trust, and accountability within AI-empowered fraud detection systems. One significant direction is the proposed model application in real-time scenarios. With its exceptional performance, implementing the Hard Voting ensemble model to oversee live transactions within the BC could prove to be profoundly beneficial. This real-time deployment could potentially deliver immediate and accurate fraud detection, thereby substantially improving the

security and dependability of BC ecosystems. Not only does the research showcase the theoretical potential of ML solutions, but also underscores the imperative need to translate these theories into practice to enhance the burgeoning domain of digital currencies.

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Breast Cancer Classification from Histopathological Images using Future Search Optimization Algorithm and Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

In medical imaging, precise recognition of Breast Cancer (BC) is a challenge due to the complications of breast tissues. Histopathological detection is still considered the standard in BC detection. Still, the dramatic increase in workload and the complexity of histopathological image (HPI) make this task labor-intensive and dependent on the pathologist, making the advance of automated and precise HPI analysis techniques needed. Due to the automated feature extraction capability, Deep Learning (DL) methods have been effectively used in different sectors, particularly in the medical imaging sector. This study develops the future search algorithm with a DL-based breast cancer detection and classification (FSADL-BCDC) method. The FSADL-BCDC technique examines HPIs to detect and classify BC. To achieve this, the FSADL-BCDC technique implements Wiener Filtering (WF)-based preprocessing to eliminate the noise in the images. Additionally, the FSADL-BCDC uses the ResNeXt method for feature extraction with a Future Search Algorithm (FSA)-based tuning procedure. For BCDC, the FSADL-BCDC technique employs a Hybrid Convolutional Neural Network along with the Long Short-Term Memory (HCNN-LSTM) approach. Finally, the Sunflower Optimization (SFO) approach adjusts the hyperparameter values of the HCNN-LSTM. The outcomes of the FSADL-BCDC are inspected on a standard medical image dataset. Extensive relational studies highlighted the improved performance of the FSADL-BCDC approach in comparison with known methods by exhibiting an output of 96.94% and 98.69% under diverse datasets.

Keywords-deep learning; breast cancer; future search algorithm; histopathological images; computer-aided diagnosis

I. INTRODUCTION

Amongst the many kinds of cancer, Breast Cancer (BC) is ranked second among women. Moreover, the death rate of BC is comparatively higher than that of other cancer types [1]. The analysis of Histopathological Images (HPIs) is the most frequently employed technique for the diagnosis of BC in healthcare. In HPI analysis, the most significant task is classification [2]. The precise and automatic classification of high-resolution HPIs is the bottleneck and cornerstone of other in-depth studies like gland segmentation, nuclei localization, and mitosis detection [3]. Presently, histopathological imaging in medical practice mostly depends on manual analysis. But, at least three issues arise from this approach. At first, the possible lack of pathologists, especially in small hospitals and less developed areas [4]. This unbalanced distribution and resource shortage becomes a critical issue to be solved. Secondly, whether the histopathologic diagnosis is incorrect or correct

relies on the long-term gathered diagnostic experience and professional knowledge of the given individual pathologist. This subjectivity has caused the growth of diagnostic inconsistencies [5]. Finally, the difficulty of the task makes pathologists liable to inattention and fatigue and so, keener to mistakes. Due to the similarity in features and irregular appearance between malignant and benign lesions, manual diagnosis is imprecise and difficult. To sort out such problems, it is vital to be precise and develop automatic HPI analytical approaches, namely classifier approaches. Computer-assisted diagnostic methods extract features from the nuclei to offer significant data to diagnose a lesion, either malignant or benign [6]. There are various clustering techniques and statistical approaches to extract features, classify, or segment nuclei [7]. In medical image diagnosis, there are several rapidly evolving techniques to classify HPIs, but there is still the need for more effective diagnosis. Complicated image-processing phases such as feature extraction, preprocessing, and segmentation are a

reason for low diagnostic accuracy. Hence, to sort out the Machine Learning (ML) problem, Deep Learning (DL) is presented to abstract the related attributes of the input raw images and utilize them for classification with more precision [8]. In DL, features are extracted through convolutional layers and assembly layers denoting more precision [9]. Currently, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are utilized to classify biomedical images. CNN works very well with huge datasets and is less precise on small datasets [10]. In small datasets, pre-trained CNNs are usually utilized.

This study introduces an innovative approach termed as Future Search Algorithm with DL-based Breast Cancer Detection and Classification (FSADL-BCDC). This technique incorporates several components to enhance its performance. At first, the FSADL-BCDC method employs Wiener Filtering (WF) as a pre-processing procedure for effective noise removal. Additionally, it leverages the ResNeXt model for feature extraction, optimizing hyperparameters using the FSA technique. For BCDC, the FSADL-BCDC method utilizes a Hybrid CNN with the Long Short-Term Memory (HCNN-LSTM) approach. To further fine-tune the HCNN-LSTM approach, the Sunflower Optimization (SFO) technique is employed for adjusting the hyperparameter values. The efficiency of the FSADL-BCDC technique is validated through experiments conducted on a well-established benchmark medical image dataset.

II. RELATED WORK

This section presents a short overview of recently developed BC classification models on HPIs. Authors in [11] developed a new CNN structure for classifying malignant and benign BC HPIs. Authors in [12] developed the AOADL-HBCC approach for making decisions. This approach uses noise removal depending on a contrast enhancement process and median filtering. Authors in [13] devised a BC-HPI classification that depends on deep FE-BkCapsNet to make full use of CapsNet and CNNs. Authors in [14] developed an automatic technique for diagnosing BC from HPIs. In this method, a residual learning-related 152-layered CNN termed ResHist was devised for classification. Authors in [15] applied ShuffleNet, Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), InceptionV3, and ResNet18 for the binary classification of BC in HPIs. They utilized pre-trained networks on the ImageNet dataset with layers given training on HPIs from BreakHis. In [16], a new technique depending on the Convolution-LSTM (CLSTM), with utilizing the Marker-controlled Watershed Segmentation Algorithm (MWSA) for preprocessing and SVM detection, was proposed. Authors in [17] focused on BC HPIs attained taking the assistance of the microscopic scan of breast tissues. The model joined two DCNNs to derive differentiated image aspects by employing TL. Authors in [18] introduced a frequency domain learning technique that relies on CNN and DWT for the classification task of BC HPIs. In [19], an enhanced model, IBESSDL-BCHI, was introduced for BC recognition by employing HPIs. The approach incorporates MF, Synergic DL (SDL), and LSTM techniques for preprocessing, tuning, and classification. Authors in [20] proposed the innovative HRLCE approach with two processing stages. Their method, the SAE-PSO-DNN model, combines

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Stacked Autoencoders (SAE) within a DNN framework.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

This article focuses on the design and development of the FSADL-BCDC approach for detecting and classifying BC. The main intention of the FSADL-BCDC method is to investigate HPIs in order to detect and classify BC. In the FSADL-BCDC method, the majorly involved procedures are WF-based preprocessing, ResNeXt feature extractor, FSA-based tuning, HCNN-LSTM classification, and SFO-based optimization. Figure 1 depicts the complete procedure of the FSADL-BCDC method.

Fig. 1. The overall process of the FSADL-BCDC approach.

A. Pre-processing

To eliminate noise from the input image, the WF technique is employed, functioning in the frequency domain of the image. The WF computes the Fourier transform of the image and the power spectrum of the noise, using a filter to reduce noise across all frequency components while preserving essential image details. In image processing, the WF curtails the mean squared error amid the original and filtered images, with adjustable filter parameters influencing performance, contingent on the accuracy of the assessed power spectrum of

the noise. Its efficacy in signal processing lies in minimizing mean square error, offering optimal linear estimation amidst noise, and its adaptability to diverse signal and noise characteristics renders it advantageous in specific applications.

B. Feature Extraction

ResNeXt method, an enhanced version of ResNet, is used for the extracting process. The parallel stacking block with a similar topology was utilized instead of the 3-layer convolution block [21]. The ResNeXt network consists of 4 ResNeXt block structures, namely 1 convolutional layer, 1 FC layer, 2 pooling layers, and 1 softmax classifier. Deep residual networking had cardinality and was composed of ResNeXt blocks. The leftover block can be changed by the split-transform-merge approach that results in branch routes within a cell. By the path of the skip connection, the output can be defined as:

$$OP = a + \sum_{i=1}^{ca} \tau_i(a) \quad (1)$$

where τ_i , ca , OP , and a denote the arbitrary conversion, cardinality, and the earlier layer's output and input.

Every ResNeXt block has 3 convolutional layers and a shortcut connection. The 3 dissimilar kinds of convolution layers are convolution, group convolution, and convolution in series. Except for the final convolution layer, ReLU function is used to improve the network's non-linearity after the convolution layer. The ResNeXt block's group convolution stride is 2. Maxpooling is used to achieve spatial invariance and accelerate training while maintaining accuracy. The essential idea behind max-pooling was selecting the discriminatory features and representing a bunch of features.

$$v_{i,L}^{x,y} = \max_{m \in [0, m_i-1], n \in [0, n_i-1]} (x+m), (y+n) (i-1), L(2)$$

where, m_i , n_i denote the size of kernels, and L is the index of the mapping features at the $(i-1)^{\text{th}}$ convolutional layer. The softmax classifier is utilized to implement the last classification. The early layers of the ResNeXt models capture simple features like edges, corners, and color gradients. The intermediate layers learn more complex features like shapes, textures, and object parts. The deeper layers can represent high-level semantic concepts and objects specific to the classes present in the ImageNet dataset.

C. Hyperparameter Tuning

In this work, the FSA optimizes the hyperparameter values in the ResNeXt approach by simulating optimal lifestyles for individuals, mapping this concept to the selection process of ResNeXt's hyperparameters. Employing a mathematical formula, the FSA enhances the initial random parameters through a global search among successful individuals and a local search within the population [22]. The FSA can be generated dependent upon mathematical formulas and begins phases depending on random solutions:

$$S(i,:) = Lb + (Ub - Lb) \times \text{rand}(1, d) \quad (3)$$

where $S(i,:)$ denotes the i^{th} solution, Lb and Ub signify the lower and upper boundaries, and rand implies the uniform distribution of a d -dimensional pseudorandom number.

Every solution is realized as the local (LS) and global (GS), solutions. Afterwards, this technique begins its iterations for determining the optimum solution. Primary, the search procedure in FSA is dependent upon the LS to assist the characteristics of exploitation.

$$S(i,:)_L = (LS(i,:) - S(i,:)) \times \text{rand} \quad (4)$$

The search procedure of FSA in the search scope is dependent upon GS assisting the exploitation feature:

$$S(i,:)_G = (GS - S(i,:)) \times \text{rand} \quad (5)$$

After estimating the local and global convergence, all the solutions are upgraded as:

$$S(i,:) = S(i,:) + S(i,:)_L + S(i,:)_G \quad (6)$$

This technique upgrades GS and LS , and every solution is upgraded as:

$$S(i,:) = GS + (GS - S(i,:)) \times \text{rand} \quad (7)$$

Lastly, the FSA will check the GS and LS and will update them if there are better solutions. The iterative procedure of FSA is projected as follows:

- Step 1. Arbitrarily determine the primary size of population, the main function, and its searching space. Fix the maximal iteration count Max . Set $t = 1$. Define the upper and lower limitations. Compute the primary GS and the primary LS . Initialize by (3).
- Step 2. The search process is dependent on LS in (4) and the global search is dependent on GS in (5). Calculate the local and global convergences. The outcome is determined in (6).
- Step 3. Relate the Fitness Function (FF) values of every possible solution to determine the GS and LS from the present generation. Compare the present GS and LS with the preceding values and upgrade if necessary. Upgrade the arbitrary primary (7).
- Step 4. Compute $t = t + 1$. See if $t = Max$. If no, then go to Step 2. Else, stop and provide the resulting outcome.

D. Image Classification: The Optimal HCNN-LSTM Model

Finally, BC classification takes place using the HCNN-LSTM approach. The LSTM mostly overcomes the problems of gradient vanishing as a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) variant, making the network more reliable and remembering the content for a long period. LSTM can be capable of removing or maximizing data [23]. LSTM consists of output, input, and forget gates, which are used for providing reset, read, and write functions. d_{t-1} shows the prior output of the model, X_t indicates the existing input used for producing novel memory, C_{t-1} denotes the prior cell state from the model, and the output data encompass the cell state C_t and the newest output d_t . A large amount of data will be flooding the memory once the input gate is opened. So, a forget gate is added for removing these data. Given X_t (existing input) and d_{t-1} (prior output), a number between 0 and 1 is acquired for all the digits at the cell state C_{t-1} (prior state), where 0 signifies completely discarded, and 1 indicates completely reserved:

$$F_t = \text{Sigmoid}(W_f[d_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (8)$$

In (8), b_f indicates the bias term, W_f shows the weight matrix, and the resultant value through this networking lies inside $[0, 1]$, which shows that the prior cell state probability has been forgotten, 1 is "fully saved" and 0 is "completely deleted".

After circulating NN's forget part of the prior state, the LSTM's input gate needs to add the new memory from the present input. This procedure should be satisfied by the input gate, which includes two segments, namely a sigmoid layer that defines which value must be renewed and a tanh layer that decides a new candidate vector \tilde{C}_t increased to this state:

$$h_t = \sigma(W_n \cdot [d_{t-1}, X_t] + b_n) \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_M \cdot [d_{t-1}, X_t] + b_m) \quad (10)$$

$$C_t = F_t \times C_{t-1} + h_t \times \tilde{C}_t \quad (11)$$

where W_n , b_m , h_t , C_t , and W_M portray the weighted matrix, the bias item to update state, the input gate, the upgraded memory unit state, and the weighted matrix to upgrade the layer. C_t takes the dot product of the forget gate F_t with C_{t-1} for determining if it remembers its value, h_t and \tilde{C}_t determine whether to upgrade C_t , and b_n symbolizes the biased item. The output gate decides the present, the newest, and the final output. The LSTM's resulting gate is the outcome of the present moment that should be produced after evaluating the newest state:

$$d_r = 0_t \times \tanh(C_t) \quad (12)$$

$$0_t = \sigma(WV_o[d_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (13)$$

where d_t is correlated to C_t and to the input x_t at the t time step and the hidden layer's value of activation d_{t-1} at the prior time-step. The sigmoid function is used to attain 0_t within $[0,1]$, and later multiplies C_t with 0_t and \tanh . The CNN and LSTM, conventional in DL models, excel in spatial abstraction/local feature extraction and sequential/temporal processing, respectively. Recent studies manage enhanced stability by merging both methods, leading this study to adopt a parallel connection for a CNN-LSTM architecture, emphasizing the interconnected features of CNN and LSTM networks [23]. Leveraging the SFO method, adjustments to hyperparameter values in the HCNN-LSTM approach mimic the daily sunflower cycle, offering an effective strategy for hyperparameter tuning in the CNN-LSTM model [24]. The amount of heat Q_i obtained by all the plants can be defined as:

$$Q_i = \frac{P}{4\pi r_i^2} \quad (14)$$

where P , r_i denote the source of power and the distance among them. The sunflower faces the sun in the succeeding path:

$$\vec{s}_i = \frac{x^* - x_i}{\|x^* - x_i\|} \text{ where } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

The sunflower direction is evaluated as:

$$d_i = \alpha \times Pi(X_i + X_i - 1) \times \||X_i + X_i - 1\| \quad (16)$$

In (16), the possibility of pollination is $Pi(\|X_i + X_i - 1\|)$ that implies the sunflower i will be pollinating its adjacent neighbor $i - l$ and generate a new one in an arbitrary location, whereas α denotes the inertial displacement. The maximal step can be formulated as:

$$d_{\max} = \frac{\|X_{\max} - X_{\min}\|}{2 \times N_{pop}} \quad (17)$$

In (17), X_{\max} and X_{\min} denote the maximum and minimum values. N_{pop} indicates the overall plant number in the population. The newest plantation can be defined by:

$$\vec{X}_{i+1} \rightarrow \vec{x}_i + d_i \times \vec{s}_i \quad (18)$$

In the SFO approach, the selection of fitness relies on evaluating the candidate goodness using an encoder output, with accuracy being the pivotal criterion for defining the FF:

$$\text{Fitness} = \max\left(\frac{TP}{TP+FP}\right) \quad (19)$$

where TP and FP characterize the True and False Positive values.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the investigational output evaluation of the FSADL-BCDC approach is experimented on the BreakHis dataset [25]. The BreakHis dataset offers a distinctive advantage by providing a comprehensive collection of histopathological imaging. Its categorization into benign and malignant tumors across multiple magnifications enhances the dataset's suitability for diverse and specialized studies. It comprises the datasets 40X and 100X magnification, consisting of 1995 and 2081 samples, respectively. In Figure 2, the relational outputs of the FSADL-BCDC method with recent models [26] are portrayed on the 40X dataset. It can be seen that the FSADL-BCDC method portrayed increased $accu_y$, $prec_n$, and $reca_l$ of 96.94%, 96.71%, and 96.94%. It can be seen that PFTAS-QDA, ResNet50, Xception, Inception-v3, and Inception-ResNetv2 approaches reached lesser $accu_y$, $prec_n$, and $reca_l$ values.

Fig. 2. Comparative analysis of the FSADL-BCDC approach on the 40X dataset.

Fig. 3. Comparative analysis of the FSADL-BCDC approach on the 100X dataset.

In Figure 3, the relative output of the FSADL-BCDC approach is given on the 100X dataset. It can be seen that the FSADL-BCDC approach offers increased $accu_y$, $prec_n$, $reca_l$ of 98.69%, 98.47%, and 98.69%, whereas the PFTAS-QDA, ResNet50, Xception, Inception-v3, and Inception-ResNetv2 approaches attained lesser $accu_y$, $prec_n$, and $reca_l$ values.

V. CONCLUSION

In this article, focus is given on the design and development of the FSADL-BCDC methodology for detecting and classifying BC from HPIs. The main objective of the FSADL-BCDC methodology is to investigate HPIs to detect and classify BC. In the FSADL-BCDC technique, the involved processes are WF-based preprocessing, ResNeXt feature extractor, FSA-based tuning, HCNN-LSTM classification, and SFO-based optimization. The utilization of the FSA and SFO techniques enhances the detection and classification performance of the FSADL-BCDC technique. The investigational outputs of the FSADL-BCDC method are examined on a standard medical image dataset. Extensive comparison studies highlighted the achievement of 96.94% and 98.69% enhanced accuracy of the proposed method under diverse data, which surpasses the considered existing techniques. Thus, the FSADL-BCDC method can be utilized for the automated classification of BC. In the future, the performance of the FSADL-BCDC method can be enhanced by the design of ensemble classifier methods. The FSADL-BCDC method may encounter challenges in handling diverse histopathological images and could be sensitive to variations in image quality. Also, the reliance on sunflower optimization for tuning may pose computational complexities and scalability issues in large-scale datasets.

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Prediction of Vehicle-induced Air Pollution based on Advanced Machine Learning Models

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ABSTRACT

Vehicle-induced air pollution is an important issue in the 21st century, posing detrimental effects on human health. Prediction of vehicle-emitted air pollutants and evaluation of the diverse factors that contribute to them are of the utmost importance. This study employed advanced tree-based machine learning models to predict vehicle-induced air pollutant levels, with a particular focus on fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). In addition to a benchmark statistical model, the models employed were Gradient Boosting (GB), Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Extra Tree (ET), and Random Forest (RF). Regarding the evaluation of PM_{2.5} predictions, the ET model outperformed the others, as shown by MAE of 1.69, MSE of 5.91, RMSE of 2.43, and R² of 0.71. Afterward, the optimal ET models were interpreted using SHAP analysis to overcome the ET model's lack of explainability. Based on the SHAP analysis, it was determined that temperature, humidity, and wind speed emerged as the primary determinants in forecasting PM_{2.5} levels.

Keywords-air pollutants; machine learning; SHAP analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Air pollution has become a prominent concern in the 21st century posing a significant threat to human health [1]. Vehicle emissions contribute significantly to atmospheric pollution in urban areas, often serving as the primary source of ultrafine particles and chemical pollutants, including carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), and Total Volatile Organic Compounds (TVOCs) [2-3]. In general, increased air pollution can be attributed to increased motorization, energy consumption, and urbanization [4]. Exposure to elevated levels of automobile exhaust pollution adversely affects human health. Numerous studies have shown a link between exposure to air pollution on heavily trafficked roads and various harmful health effects, including elevated risk of mortality [5-6], higher rates of cardiopulmonary

mortality [7], higher incidence of coronary heart disease [8], impaired respiratory function such as wheezing and reduced peak respiratory flow during infancy [9], lung cancer [10], pulmonary edema [11], allergic alveolitis [12], and development of chronic bronchitis and asthma [13]. Higher incidences of these health effects have been observed in cities that rely on automobiles for daily transportation due to inadequate public transport [14]. It is important to recognize that some of the other factors that contribute to these emissions include the presence of old and deteriorated engines, the use of improper fuel grades, the lack of routine maintenance, engine degradation over time, excessive vehicle use, mishandling of lubricants, and limitations in achieving optimal fuel combustion [15]. In addition to these factors, meteorological factors have been proven to influence the concentration and spread of air pollutants.

Air pollution modeling can describe the causal relationship between emissions, meteorology, atmospheric concentrations, deposition, and other aspects. Air quality modeling aims to forecast the dispersion, spatial distribution, and concentration of atmospheric pollutants using mathematical or statistical methods that replicate physical and chemical processes [16]. Currently, there is widespread adoption of Machine Learning (ML) techniques for air quality forecasting. ML is a computational approach to extracting information from data, characterized by its ability to autonomously adjust its algorithms and models in response to new datasets, requiring minimal initial configuration [17]. The typical steps in this process involve data collection, screening model evaluation, analysis using a complex model and algorithm, and finally evaluation and verification of the model's output. Although ML has proven to be effective in making predictions, one of its major disadvantages is its black-box nature. Therefore, the post hoc SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) [18] technique has been used to explain models from both a global and a local perspective. SHAP is normally used to make an ML model more explicable by visualizing its output. Due to the high efficiency of SHAP in interpreting various ML models, it has been used in several fields, such as the safety assessment of infrastructure projects [19], clinical medicine and healthcare modeling [20-21], transportation and traffic safety [22-25], and economic risk analysis [26].

ML techniques have been used by many studies in air quality modeling and prediction, facilitated by the transition from manual to automated methods. In [27], roadside air pollution in Lisbon, Portugal, was modeled by training ML models with data from meteorological sensors and mobile monitoring stations, showing that the Random Forest (RF) algorithm was more effective in forecasting pollutant concentrations. In [28], data from fixed monitoring stations and meteorological sensors were used to perform deep learning-based prediction, showing that a Support Vector Regression (SVR) model was the best in predicting pollutant concentrations. In [29], air pollution levels in Delhi, India, were predicted using data from fixed monitoring stations and meteorological sensors, showing that a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Network (NN) was best suited to predict pollutant concentrations. In [16], ML algorithms were used to predict traffic-related particulate matter pollution in Sao Paulo, Brazil, using data from fixed monitoring stations and traffic sensors and showing that SVR was the best in predicting pollutant concentrations. Some studies used sophisticated methods, such as ensemble learning classification systems, to predict air quality [30]. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have also been popular techniques in predicting air pollution [31-33]. In general, ML algorithms can be effective in simulating and forecasting levels of roadside air pollution and can be used to create more precise and effective air quality monitoring systems.

This study used different ML algorithms, including Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [34], RF [35], Extra Tree (ET) [36], Gradient Boosting (GB) [37], and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM) [38], which were optimized using a Bayesian optimization approach [39]. These models were trained and evaluated using data on vehicle-

induced air pollutants, specifically $PM_{2.5}$, collected from the JKIA-Westlands expressway corridor in Kenya. Additionally, a statistical multivariate linear regression model was used as a benchmark model. This study used Bayesian optimization and ML regression models in conjunction with SHAP analysis to determine the optimal regression model for the dataset. This amalgamation was expected to provide a reliable and accurate method for evaluating vehicle-induced air pollutants. Figure 1 shows the complete research process.

Fig. 1. Research framework.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Site and Data Collection

Data were collected at three locations along the JKIA-Westlands Expressway in Kenya, as shown in Figure 2: Westlands, Bellevue, and City Cabanas. The Westlands location has mixed commercial and residential land use whereas City Cabanas is a predominantly industrial area and has commercial land use. The Bellevue station is close to the city center and characterized by residential and commercial land use. Data were collected 24/7 during August 2022, December 2022, and February 2023. Traffic volume was collected using manual traffic counts that were recorded every 15 minutes and summarized as hourly traffic volume. Various vehicle classifications were recorded: motorcycles, cars, minibuses, buses, light-goods vehicles, medium-goods vehicles, heavy-goods vehicles, and articulated trucks. In addition to documenting traffic volume, the study simultaneously collected data on air pollutant concentrations, average vehicle speed, and meteorological data, such as humidity, wind speed, and temperature. Air quality was measured using Open-Seneca sensors for each second. Air quality data includes the concentrations of Particulate Matter ($PM_{1.0}$, $PM_{2.5}$, $PM_{4.0}$, PM_{10}), Typical Particle Size (TPS), Number of Concentrations of particles ($NC_{1.0}$, $NC_{2.5}$, $NC_{4.0}$, NC_{10}), TVOC, and equivalent CO_2 . The air quality data was then averaged to the hourly data so that a comparison could be made between air quality, hourly traffic, and meteorological data. Regarding air quality data, this study focused exclusively on $PM_{2.5}$.

Fig. 2. Data collection sites along the JKIA-Westlands Expressway (ArcGIS 10.5.1).

B. Model Development

A statistical multiple variable Linear Regression (LR) model and five advanced ML models (GB, XGBoost, RF, ET, and LGBM) were used to forecast $PM_{2.5}$. Python 3.7.1 was used to implement the models and Bayesian optimization was used to tune their hyperparameters. Figure 3 illustrates the procedure involved in developing the ML models.

Fig. 3. Flow diagram of ML modeling, showing input and output variables.

C. Gradient Boosting (GB)

GB is an ML algorithm that gradually merges multiple weak learners into a single robust one. The following are the necessary steps in GB: Start by making a simple tree with only one root node that is the first impression of each sample. Next, use the flawed nodes to build a new tree. Sort the branches by how quickly they learn (the value is usually between 0 and 1). This learning rate will be used as input to the tree for the forecast. Then, combine the newly constructed tree with the older trees to make a prediction. If the fit has not improved after a certain number of trees was added, return to the second step. The combined set of trees is the prediction model.

D. Random Forest (RF)

The RF regression model is a collection of multiple decision trees that function as parallel estimators. The result is determined by aggregating the majority vote of the results obtained from each decision tree. The efficiency of an RF model depends on the utilization of uncorrelated decision trees. The training phase for each decision tree is improved by incorporating bootstrapping and feature randomness. The bootstrapping process involves the random selection of samples from a given training dataset with replacement. On the other hand, feature randomness is achieved by randomly selecting a subset of features for each decision tree within the RF model. Consequently, the base estimators exhibit independence and identical distribution, which leads to improved performance when subjected to the bagging technique.

E. Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost)

XGBoost regression employs the technique of gradient descent on decision trees to iteratively generate a series of models. These models are subsequently combined sequentially, with each model aiming to rectify the errors made by the previous models. The ultimate objective is to produce a final model that is optimized for the given task. XGBoost demonstrates high efficiency in terms of computational resource utilization and processing speed.

F. Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM) Regression

This framework uses tree-based learning to achieve efficient and distributed boosting. LGBM employs a leaf-wise growth strategy to construct the tree, in which a tree is generated for each individual sample. The selection of the leaf is determined by the maximum potential for growth inhibition. The leaf-wise algorithm exhibits less loss compared to the level-wise tree algorithm due to the fixed nature of the leaf. Therefore, the growth of trees in a leaf-wise manner results in heightened complexity in the model and occasionally results in overfitting when applied to datasets of limited size. LGBM aims to decrease complexity through the use of gradient-based one-side sampling and exclusive feature bundling.

G. Multivariate Linear Regression (MLR)

MLR is a widely used technique in supervised ML that examines the relationship between a group of independent variables or features and a singular outcome variable. This technique uses mathematical equations to represent and predict outcomes, particularly in cases where the correlation coefficient between the variables suggests a statistically significant association.

H. Extra Tree (ET) Regression

The ET algorithm was created to mitigate the risk of overfitting the dataset. Like RF, ET uses a random subset of features to train each base estimator. The selection of the optimal feature and value for node partitioning is carried out randomly.

I. Bayesian Optimization

Bayesian optimization strategy was used to fine-tune the hyperparameters in the models. This algorithm uses ideas from the Bayesian theorem and is recognized as a prominent method

for achieving global optimization. Bayesian optimization has been extensively used in various disciplines [40]. Optimization of the hyperparameters of the model involves maximization or minimization of the objective function. Consequently, the algorithm identifies the suitable combination of hyperparameters that guarantees that the model's performance is maximized to its utmost potential. This study uses R^2 as the evaluation metric.

J. SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP)

SHAP is a post hoc evaluation of ML models based on the game theory [18]. SHAP employs an additive factor attribution method to generate a coherent model. SHAP values improve the model's transparency and give insight into the functioning of the prediction model. Through the SHAP feature importance plot, significant features are selected based on the Shapley values. The feature effects and feature importance are combined in the summary plot, which indicates the correlation between a feature's value and its impact on the prediction. In this study, SHAP calculates the contribution of each feature to the prediction, which seeks to explain the prediction of an instance of air quality.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table I presents the descriptive statistics of multiple input factors.

TABLE I. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF INPUT FACTORS

Factors	Statistics			
	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max
Humidity	35.52	12.95	13.33	68.16
Temperature	26.75	4.53	16.86	42.07
Average traffic volume	1377.05	653.16	340	3211
Average vehicle speed	44.41	7.71	22.70	60.18
Wind speed	4.61	1.83	0.95	9.75
Location	0.98	0.81	0	2

The dataset used to predict air pollutant concentrations was divided into two subsets: a training-validation set, which accounted for 70% of the total data, and a testing/holdout set, which was 30% of the total data. The training-validation dataset was used for the development of the ML models and Bayesian optimization. The objective of Bayesian optimization was to determine the optimal hyperparameter configuration for different ML models to maximize the R^2 value within a specified sample space. Table II presents the optimal hyperparameter values obtained for $PM_{2.5}$.

TABLE II. ML ALGORITHMS WITH THEIR OPTIMAL HYPERPARAMETERS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF $PM_{2.5}$

Models	Hyperparameters	Range	Optimal values
LGBM	{(learning rate), (n_estimators)}	{(0.01-0.1), (50-500)}	{0.01, 92}
GB	{(learning rate), (n_estimators)}	{(0.01-0.2), (50-500)}	{0.08, 100}
RF	{(max_depth)}	{2-16}	{7}
XGBoost	{(learning rate), (n_estimators)}	{(0.01-0.2), (50-500)}	{0.07, 160}
ET	{(max_depth)}	{2-16}	{11}

A. Prediction of $PM_{2.5}$

Following the determination of the optimal hyperparameters, the holdout or testing data was used to compare the performance of the models. The dataset was divided into partitions after randomization, with 40% and 50% of the data allocated for testing. This analysis showed that the metric values for model testing remained consistent within the 95% confidence interval. This precautionary step was implemented to mitigate the risk of overfitting. No anomalies were observed in the performance metrics, regardless of the size of the test data. Table III presents the efficiency metrics for $PM_{2.5}$ prediction, using both training and test datasets. The ET model exhibited superior performance compared to the others, as shown by its lower Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of 1.69, Mean Squared Error (MSE) of 5.91, Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of 2.43, and higher R^2 of 0.711. The linear regression model showed the poorest performance, having 3.57 MAE, 19.11 MSE, 4.37 RMSE, and 0.064 R^2 . Prediction error plots were used, as shown in Figure 4, to evaluate the efficiency of the ML regression models in predicting $PM_{2.5}$ and their ability to make predictions on unobserved data.

Fig. 4. Prediction Error for $PM_{2.5}$: (a) XGBoost, (b) RF, (c) LightGBM, (d) GB, (e) ET, and (f) LR.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE USING ML AND STATISTICAL MODELS FOR PREDICTING PM_{2.5}

Training dataset				
Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R ²
RF	1.73	5.5	2.35	0.73
XGBoost	1.36	4.78	2.18	0.77
LGBM	1.73	5.56	2.35	0.73
GB	2.03	6.89	2.62	0.67
ET	1.48	4.92	2.22	0.76
LR	3.53	19.1	4.37	0.09
Testing dataset				
Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	R-Square
RF	2.06	7.11	2.66	0.652
XGBoost	1.64	6.57	2.56	0.678
LGBM	2.04	7.19	2.68	0.648
GB	2.35	8.69	2.94	0.575
ET	1.69	5.91	2.43	0.711
LR	3.57	19.11	4.37	0.064

B. Global Interpretation by SHAP

The decision to employ ET as a fitting method for PM_{2.5}, considering the given factors, was determined based on its R² value. The analysis of the ET prediction for PM_{2.5} yields insights into the global factor interpretation, as shown in Figure 5, which illustrates the significance and contribution of the SHAP factors. The mean absolute SHAP value shown in Figure 5(a) signifies the average influence on the magnitude of the model's output.

Fig. 5. Global factor interpretation: (a) Factor importance plot, and (b) contribution plot for PM_{2.5}.

Humidity had the highest SHAP significance score of 1.35, while temperature had 0.84 and Wind Speed had 0.55. The dots that exhibit a color gradient from purple to red, descending to the right of the vertical reference line denoting humidity, indicate an elevated level of PM_{2.5} risk. Similarly, the dots that symbolize low-temperature values are situated to the right of the vertical reference line, suggesting a higher likelihood for PM_{2.5} to escalate. The findings indicate higher accuracy and reliability due to the use of ML, which is consistent with the

findings from earlier studies on air quality prediction [27-31]. SHAP was useful in determining the degree to which the input parameters had an impact on the forecasts, which is consistent with prior studies that used SHAP analysis to gather local information about the factors causing either greater or lower pollutant concentrations [41-42]. Therefore, SHAP analysis provided an effective method for addressing the issue of limited interpretability inherent in ML regression models.

IV. CONCLUSION

From the analyzed results, the following deductions can be made:

- According to the collected dataset, ET exhibited superior performance compared to the other models, as demonstrated by its lower MAE (1.69), MSE (5.91), RMSE (2.43), and higher R² value (0.711). The linear regression model exhibited the poorest performance, as shown by its MAE (3.57), MSE (19.11), RMSE (4.37), and R² (0.064).
- In the context of PM_{2.5} humidity, temperature, and wind speed were found to have the most significant influence.
- Bayesian optimization improved the prediction by selecting the important features, which resulted in better predictive results. This is in agreement with [43], who obtained better results using an improved collection of characteristics to predict cardiovascular diseases.
- Undoubtedly, ML is a highly valuable resource with many benefits in different fields, including medicine [43-44], information technology [45], and transportation [23, 25]. The findings indicate that ML has the potential to be used to predict roadside air pollution.

However, it is important to consider several suggestions for future research endeavors:

- Although this study employed various input parameters to predict PM_{2.5}, it is important to note that several additional factors could be considered in future investigations.
- This study focused solely on predicting PM_{2.5}. However, it should be noted that future studies could potentially explore the prediction of CO, NO₂, TVOCs, and SO₂.

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Empowering Learning through Intelligent Data-Driven Systems

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ABSTRACT

The evolution of educational systems is closely tied to technological advancements, particularly the emergence of machine learning. This technology offers a sophisticated system capable of predicting, explaining, and influencing behavior. Many efforts have aimed to integrate machine learning into education, focusing on specific cases using ad-hoc models. This paper introduces an intelligent educational system that relies on data-driven student models, aiming to surpass the limitations of these ad-hoc systems. The approach outlined in this endeavor adopts a comprehensive and methodical modeling methodology centered on machine learning techniques. By employing Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), the proposed approach enables predictive student models based on historical educational data. The effectiveness of this method was tested through experimentation on an intelligent tutoring system using 5-fold cross-validation, revealing that the smart educational system achieved a remarkable 96% accuracy rate. Furthermore, a comparison between the importance scores of features with and without the student models demonstrated the practicality and effectiveness of the proposed methodology.

Keywords-machine learning; educational systems; CNN; historical data

I. INTRODUCTION

Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITSs) are the subject of many computer-aided systems that automatically provide teaching and training [1]. These systems require considerable knowledge in computer science, even psychological interaction. Artificial Intelligence (AI) allowed a significant revolution in education, ensuring complex cognitive skills [2]. The ITS based-AI is a computer program using computational models that enable detailed feedback with customized instruction. Developed ITSs are applied to various educational systems and millions of learners worldwide [4-6]. Learners using ITSs are motivated to know what they learn, how to learn, and whom they learn through reasoning techniques incorporated in ITSs. These features are based on four models [3]:

- The student model stores nationality and the current state to choose a suitable new problem.
- The domain model stores knowledge.
- The user interface provides access to the domain knowledge elements.
- The tutor model stores pedagogical knowledge.

The student model is the most important key to the success of an ITS [7, 8]. It should be able not only to support the students' skills and behaviors but also to provide the students' performance and abilities according to knowledge level and educational background. Authors in [6] focused on the dynamic characteristics of the tutor. They studied many features,

including skills, knowledge, misconceptions, preferences, and learning styles. They highlighted two dynamic concepts: (1) cognitive factors: attention, ability to solve problems and ability to learn features and (2) meta-cognitive factors: self-assessment, self-regulation, help-seeking, and attitude. Authors in [9] proposed an ITS permitting prediction, explanation, and tutor behavior using machine learning techniques. Authors in [10] presented an intelligent marine traffic simulator to provide a highly qualified system for trainees and students. The author's objectives focus on enhancing learning skills in a safe condition and providing intelligent decision-making support for collision avoidance. Authors in [11] listed many studies related to ITS based on machine learning. These attempts aimed to model an application-based cognitive process assessment and prediction for specific cases. Authors in [12] presented a prediction model to study the student's performance. Their attempt used clustering methods to identify learning difficulties. Authors in [13] predicted tutors' effortful behavior using the pipeline grey-box approach, allowing the prediction of performance related to assessment tasks. Authors in [3] summarized the student modeling technique. They aimed to provide an accurate elaborative environment, corrective strategy, and evaluative models. Authors in [14] proposed an outcome-based education model to support the accreditation process. They focused on the subject quality, faculty experience, and student quality factors to perform course learning outcomes measurement. The proposed model attempted to identify the most suitable weight of each factor. Authors in [15] focused on working conditions related to real

and natural educational contexts. They proved that there is a complicated landscape regarding the effectiveness of ITS in real educational contexts. They found that there is a noticeable disparity in the regions where studies on ITS using social experiments were carried out.

The above studies proved that a successful ITS has to include predictive student modeling. The model must identify latent constructs and future outcomes (failure or success in a course) [16]. Nevertheless, the developed models used only one machine learning technique and are considered for specific domain data. This paper deals with this issue and provides systemic and comprehensive machine learning and ensures an accurate and smart learner model for predicting tutors' learning performance. The idea covers building data-driven student models according to models related to knowledge or domain theory. The present paper proposes an innovative and powerful approach to ensure a high-performance student model supporting static and dynamic features during the learning process. Static features are defined as student profile information and dynamic features describe the student's behavior, including attention during the interaction with the ITS. This paper attempts to improve the student model by using machine learning applied to the historical and educational data. To address the above challenge, the following points are tackled:

- Building a data-driven student model according to a comprehensive student modeling methodology.
- Obtaining high accuracy of the student model built according to the historical data.
- Determining the more significant features to understand the student model's utility.

To achieve the objectives of this paper, we proceed with the following contributions:

- A student model based on a comprehensive machine learning approach is proposed.
- The proposed model is verified through a case study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A student model-based on AI is focused on human or social behavior [9]. According to the historical data collected from the user, the model is built using a variety of machine-learning algorithms. In this section, we highlight the methodology of the proposed tutoring system. The model is composed of four steps, described in Figure 1:

- The preprocessing step ensures that only significant data are retrieved and considered in the training step. Building a relevant dataset is important to achieve an accurate prediction. The preprocessing step attempts to find significant data through large amounts of data. Our system retrieved data related to student learning behavior and external impact elements during the preprocessing. The dataset contained student profile, course object, teaching techniques, environment features, and learning behavior (problem-solving capabilities, working level, curiosity, subjects' interest, attention, etc.).
- The data augmentation step ensured the generation of more features with high quality. These new features are powerful because they are based on combinations of the initial data inputs. A risk feature is added according to the information of the domain knowledge. The data augmentation step also guarantees the selection of relevant features using the ranking method [17, 18].
- The learning algorithm step provided the most suitable model for the deployment. Many techniques can be used either in classification or regression. A model is adopted once the used learning algorithm achieves high accuracy. In our case, we used the following learning algorithms: Naïve Bayes (NB) [19], Decision Tree (DT) [20], Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [21], Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [22, 23], and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [24]. We have to highlight that for every algorithm, a customized configuration was considered in order to obtain better performance according to performance parameters referred to in [25].

Fig. 1. The machine learning model for model training.

The evaluation step showed the differences between the models. Consequently, the more suitable model could be chosen based on those results. The evaluation was performed using various criteria. For the classification task, the used metrics were ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristics) curve, AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve), ROCCH (ROC Convex Hull), DEA (Data Envelopment Analysis), accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, etc. For the regression task, the evaluation metrics included the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), the Sum of Squared Error (SSE), the Mean Squared Error (MSE), the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE).

According to the training results, the model with the higher validation score will be deployed into the ITS. This is ensured by an auto-updating model aiming to configure and replace out-mode/out-date data-driven models. Then, the feature inspection is provided by selecting the important features using MDG (Mean Decrease in Gini Impurity), MDA (Mean Decrease in Accuracy) methods [26], and the permutation importance method [27]. In our case, the features are selected based on an ordered list of features sorted according to their importance score. This method allows the teachers/instructors/trainers to understand the student model reasoning and permit the right decision.

III. RESULTS

In this section, the proposed intelligent learning tutoring system is presented, and the experimentation and performance results are detailed.

A. Case Study

The feasibility and performance of the proposed machine learning system are detailed through an intelligent tutoring system for colleges in this section. The student model is built according to the suggested model considering the ITS data. The sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy metrics are considered for evaluation. The developed model is shown in Figure 2. The model is composed of three layers: GUI, Model, and Data Access layers. The GUI layer defines the graphic training instruction/interaction interface between the trainee and the ITS system. The model layer consists of the trainee model, the trainee profile, training strategies, and the knowledge domain.

The proposed model described in Figure 2 shows that the intelligent learning tutoring system can train trainees with different educational backgrounds and experiences. All information related to the trainee is kept in the trainee profile. The system allows failure to catch up and acquire the requested skills. The data collection is proceeded using data-driven trainee/student models. The training data for each training object were collected with a given sampling rate. The variable data used during the training in the tutoring system are shown in Table I. The educational background Eb is a normalized feature that refers to the degree of education and the major subject. One training object is adopted to ensure relevant data with the instructor's outcome. The outcome Out variable indicates the failure or the success of the trainee/student. This paper is focused on classification-based models. It aims to predict the outcomes through the student profile, training object identifier, course object, learning behavior, and situations.

Fig. 2. The intelligent learning tutoring systems

The description information of each training object is detailed in Table I. The retained data after the selection phase are 2452 samples. The built dataset validates the student model through the proposed machine learning methods.

TABLE I. COLLECTED DATA VARIABLES FROM THE TUTORING SYSTEM

Data source	Variables	Attribute name	Type
Student profile	Eb	Education background	Nominal
	Age	Age	Numeric
	Sex	Sex	Nominal
	Nat	Nationality	Nominal
	Rs	Residence state	Nominal
Training object identifier	DT	Date and Time	Date/time
	Cn	Course name	Text
	Teach	Teacher name	Text
Course object	Gl	Grade level	Numeric
	Univ	University	Nominal
	Sd	Study discipline	Nominal
	Bk	Background knowledge	Nominal
	Cobj	Course objectives	Numeric
Learning behavior	ILs	Interest level in the subject	Nominal
	Hw	Hardworking	Nominal
	Rc	Retake the course	Numeric
	Ls	Learning strategy	Nominal
	Sl	Speed learning	Nominal
Situations	Td	Target diploma	Nominal
	Old	Outcomes learnings degree	Numeric
	Pr	Presence rate	Numeric
	Sp	Student position	Numeric
	Risk	Risk feature (new feature)	Numeric
Learning results	Cf	Confidence	Numeric
	Out	Outcome	Nominal

B. Experiments and Results

Based on the above dataset, the student model describes the learning behavior and predicts outcomes (Failure/Success) according to the machine learning methodology proposed above.

In the first step, preprocessing, the collected data shown in Table I have to be assigned to right values of the raw data. In the hardworking attribute case, the type is defined as a nominal variable assigned by the instructor according to the assessment report: The value is assigned to three states: High, Medium,

and Low. Other attributes with nominal values are treated similarly.

In the second step, feature processing, the trainee model generates the new features titled risk based on basic knowledge. The risk feature is calculated based on (1). The risk feature is computed to give a precise idea about the failure risk and enhance the model performance. The risk feature is processed through the course objectives and outcomes the trainee/student achieves for every course.

$$R_f = 1 - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C_{i_{obj}/Trainee}}{C_{i_{obj}}} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of courses, $C_{i_{obj}/Trainee}$ is the rate of achieved objectives in a course, and $C_{i_{obj}}$ is the course objectives.

This work considers the risk high when R_f is inferior to 0.3. Therefore, the risk is a subjective attribute. The model is built according to the developed above modeling methodology. The model experimentation is ensured using the WEKA tool [28]. The classification performance is computed through the following machine learning algorithms: NB, DT, SVM, CNN, and LSTM. We highlight that these algorithms provide an easy deployment in the education system. Each algorithm is used in two versions: (1) default and (2) Cost Matrix configurations. The second version considers the unexpected predictions and the sample weight to ensure an updated model behavior. Ten models are trained in our case. Five-fold cross-validation is conducted to obtain accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity metrics (Table II). The Cost Matrix version may either enhance or degrade performance. The LSTM algorithm with the Cost Matrix version achieves the best performance with 96% accuracy, 96% sensitivity, and 95% specificity. The results (Table II) prove that the proposed machine learning-based student modeling is valuable and feasible.

TABLE II. PERFORMANCE RESULTS

Student Model	ML algorithms	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity
SM1	NB	89%	90%	87%
SM2	NB Cost Matrix	92%	91%	91%
SM3	DT	79%	78%	82%
SM4	DT Cost Matrix	88%	85%	83%
SM5	SVM	90%	90%	88%
SM6	SVM Cost Matrix	82%	80%	85%
SM7	CNN	92%	92%	93%
SM8	CNN Cost Matrix	90%	92%	92%
SM9	LSTM	94%	93%	94%
SM10	LSTM Cost Matrix	96%	96%	95%

IV. DISCUSSION

The model prediction suggests selecting the student's right course and learning objects. The student model can provide right decision-making up to 96%. It helps the teacher to enhance course objects related to appropriate students and deliver proper recommendations. Therefore, the model prediction provides an intelligent tutoring system for the teacher to know the best way to instruct the students/ trainees. The feature importance is computed through the permutation importance method. Features entered to the LSTM Cost Matrix

algorithm are ranked based on the importance score, see Table III. We remark that the student models are deeply associated with high score features. These interesting results are highlighted for the following features: risk, education background, background knowledge, and learning strategy. These features are essential to build the proper training course object for different students. Some features are irrelevant to the student model's performance and will be ignored during the deployment phase. The attained objective achieved during this research is to develop a classification-based model to predict the outcome of learning performance. The proposed machine learning-based methods inform about the impact of the student models in the education system.

TABLE III. FEATURES ASSOCIATED WITH THE IMPORTANCE SCORE RANKING

Data source	Features	Variables
Student profile	Eb	82
	Age	61
	Sex	64
	Nat	43
Training object identifier	Rs	21
	DT	0.03
	Cn	0.01
Course object	Teach	0.02
	Gl	58
	Univ	11
	Sd	64
	Bk	86
Learning behavior	Cobj	55
	ILs	62
	Hw	35
	Rc	45
	Ls	92
Situations	Sl	33
	Td	20
	Old	49
	Pr	64
	Sp	60
	Risk	97

A comparison of the importance score ranking features with and without the student models is conducted based on students' feedback. Asking the same trainees to use the same learning is difficult and restricted to only 10 students. It would be necessary to highlight that this comparison gives us general information about the usefulness of the proposed model. It would be degraded due to the variation of student skills over the years.

Figure 3 shows the similarity between results with/without the student's model. The proposed student's model accurately predicts and highlights the most relevant features. In the case of features without the student's model, we remark that sex, presence, and course name are relevant features that are wrong. This misunderstanding proves the value of the proposed intelligent student model. The most pertinent features are similar for the two cases.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper presents a novel Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS) that leverages machine learning-based student models. The approach taken in this study involved the

construction of student models based on historical educational data, marking a significant departure from traditional methods. This approach aimed to enhance the understanding of students' learning patterns and needs. The practical application of these

models within the ITS framework was demonstrated through a compelling case study that utilized stored features. This application sheds light on the practicality and potential benefits of using student models in the context of intelligent tutoring.

Fig. 3. The importance score ranking of features with/without the student's models

To validate the efficacy and feasibility of this approach, a rigorous experimentation process was carried out, employing the 5-fold cross-validation technique. The experimental results provided strong support for the proposed methodology. They revealed that the machine learning-based student models built upon historical educational data have the potential to significantly enhance the effectiveness of ITS systems.

As we turn our gaze toward future endeavors in this field, a notable challenge comes into focus. This challenge revolves around the development of models that can facilitate the transfer of student models from one educational domain to another. While the current research has demonstrated the promise of machine learning-based student models within a specific domain, the ability to extend this success to different educational contexts presents an intriguing avenue for further exploration. Solving this challenge could pave the way for even more versatile and adaptive ITS systems, thereby offering an even more comprehensive and tailored learning experience for students across a wide spectrum of disciplines. This direction holds the potential to make ITSs not only more effective, but also more widely applicable, ultimately benefiting a broader range of learners.

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Mitigating Reflection Cracking in Asphalt Concrete Overlays with ECC and Geotextile

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ABSTRACT

The rehabilitation of deteriorated pavements using Asphalt Concrete (AC) overlays consistently confronts the reflection cracking challenge, where inherent cracks and joints from an existing pavement layer are mirrored in the new overlay. To address this issue, the current study evaluates the effectiveness of Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC) and geotextile fabric as mitigation strategies. ECC, characterized by its tensile ductility, fracture resistance, and high deformation capacity, was examined in interlayer thicknesses of 7, 12, and 17 mm. Additionally, the impact of geotextile fabric positioning at the base and at 1/3 depth of the AC specimen was explored. Utilizing the Overlay Testing Machine (OTM) for evaluations, the research demonstrated that ECC17 significantly mitigated reflection cracking, showing a notable 764% increase in the number of load cycles to failure (Nf) compared to the Geotextile Base (GB) specimen. Against the Reference Specimen (RS), ECC17 exhibited a remarkable 1307% enhancement in Nf values, underscoring its effectiveness. Geotextile fabric, particularly at 1/3 depth, demonstrated notable resistance but was overshadowed by the performance of ECC interlayers. The results clearly indicate that ECC, especially ECC17, stands out as an effective solution for mitigating reflection cracking, including joints, in AC overlays.

Keywords-reflection cracking; asphalt concrete overlay; geotextile; engineered cementitious composite; overlay testing machine

I. INTRODUCTION

Applying Asphalt Concrete (AC) overlays is the most commonly used method for rehabilitating deteriorated pavements. However, they do not often perform as satisfactorily as expected because of the existing cracks that propagate through the newly constructed overlay within a short period of time (reflection cracking). This phenomenon is widespread and is considered one of the most dominant existing pavement problems [1, 2]. Reflection cracking is caused by one or more cycles of thermal contraction, repeated traffic loads, or by a combination of both. Cracks in old

pavements frequently spread to the surface within one to five years if the new overlay is bonded to the damaged layer [3, 4]. Reflection cracks significantly shorten the road lifespan and make its maintenance more complex and expensive. This results in water entering the pavement structure, contributing to pavement deterioration forms, namely increased roughness, spalling, and decreased fatigue life [5]. Existing design methods do not generally provide criteria to mitigate reflection cracking. Aiming to minimize or delay this problem occurrence, techniques such as overlay thickness increase, modification of the asphalt properties, and placement of stress-

relieving interlayers have been attempted, showing, though, limited success [6].

Numerous strategies have been used to control the growth of reflection cracks as a result of the problem's aggravation. Some of these techniques, such as increasing the thickness of the overlay, modification of asphalt properties, and placement

of stress-relieving interlayers, have successfully decreased reflective cracking in particular situations, but the degree of success is usually limited. Other methods employed to alleviate reflective cracking complications, include saw and seal, fractured slabs, and many forms of interlayers. Table I provides a summary of the treatment methods discussed in the literature, along with ways to prevent reflective cracking.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR MITIGATING REFLECTIVE CRACKING

Treatment Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Increasing the thickness of the asphalt overlay [8-9]	When using comparable asphalt materials, thicker overlays perform better than thinner ones.	This is not a cost-effective approach because more overlays require more material
Crack and seat [10-11]	This is economical and appropriate for asphalt surfaces with cracks	Reflection cracking could be still occurred.
Rubblisation [12-13]	Rubblisation reduces the possibility of moving underneath the asphalt overlay, thus providing a successful strategy for delaying reflective cracking.	It isn't recommended to overlay the existing concrete pavements containing steel reinforcement.
Strain Alleviating Membranes Interlayer (SAMI) [14]	This method is considered the solution to prevent reflective cracking for up to five years	It cannot prevent reflective cracking when significant traffic loads (such as aircraft) are anticipated.
Application of asphalt geosynthetics within or underneath asphalt layers [15-16]	It is considered an efficient technique	Uncertainties exist regarding the best location for installing the geosynthetic layers for the best results.
Crack relieving interlayers [17]	This technique can be classified as a solution of short-term	The reflective cracks cannot be removed by it. It suggests combining this method with other immediate solutions for a better result.

The majority of the methods illustrated above are either ineffective or only extend the pavement overlay service by a few years. The treatment process commonly used to control reflection fractures has been extensively studied through lab tests [18], finite element simulations [19], and test road constructions [20]. These findings demonstrate that despite the semi-rigid base material high strength, the pavement is easily deformed and contracts with changes in humidity and temperature, leading to transverse contraction cracks [21]. One of the newly proposed techniques is using bendable concrete or Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECCs), placed between the existing pavement and the actual overlay. Commonly, ECC is composed of portland cement type 1, low calcium Class-F fly ash, or other pozzolanic materials. It may also encompass fine silica sand, Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) fibers, or other high tensile strength fibers, water, and superplasticizer. The PVA can make the concrete more flexible, and thus bendable [22-24]. Bendable concrete utilization provides several advantages compared to conventional concrete, including increased flexibility, reduced weight (by 20 to 40%), and increased crack resistance. Additionally, this concrete type has the ability to heal itself and does not emit the hazardous gases that are created when manufacturing conventional concrete. However, similarly to the other methods employed to mitigate reflective cracking, bendable concrete entails certain drawbacks. It has a higher beginning cost than conventional concrete, despite the fact that it can lower the overall project cost. Moreover, skilled labor is necessary for its construction while ECC quality is influenced by the materials utilized and the present environmental conditions [24, 25].

Several studies suggest additional ways to control the reflected cracking problem. For instance, geotextiles have rather strong mechanical properties, are resistant to biodegradation, and offer cost-effective solutions for applications in civil engineering [26]. Geotextiles require less skill to install

and are more affordable than conventional materials, such as concrete and gravel [27]. Additionally, by avoiding the intermixing of the base layer and subgrade particles, geotextiles can improve pavement performance while saving time and cost by reducing the requirement for excavation.

Geotextiles in pavement construction are growing in popularity as this method has proven to be effective [28]. Geotextiles have different functions as those of separation / stabilization applications, reinforcement, and filtration, while they can be laid beneath both paved and unpaved roadways. They can be used in place of or in addition to natural aggregate building materials to address cost and environmental considerations [28]. Authors in [29] explored a wide range of stressors, involving those related to building highways. They found that the subgrade soil, which serves as the pavement foundation, has a significant impact on flexible pavement performance. Moreover, it is constant across a wide range of soil types and less susceptible to the environment. In this study, various combinations of non-woven geotextiles were employed. The Indian Standard Code (IS: 2720) was followed to conduct the tests for compaction, soaking CBR, and Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS) [29]. On the other hand, geotextiles have some drawbacks as they can be affected by chemicals, moisture, and UV radiation. The fibers may degrade over time, decreasing the material functionality. Additionally, geotextiles are less load-bearing than conventional materials like concrete and gravel and might not be appropriate for uses where a large load-carrying capacity is needed. Therefore, it is crucial to choose a geotextile that is strong enough to resist the project site environmental factors and capable of withstanding the project load requirements [30, 31].

The aim of this research is to experimentally investigate the effect of EEC and geotextile materials on the mitigation of

reflective cracks. The experimental work included the utilization of ECC interlayers of thicknesses of 7, 12, and 17 mm as well as geotextile fabric positioning (at base and at 1/3 depth from the base of the asphalt concrete specimen).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC)

The raw materials selected to prepare the ECC mix for this research comprised Portland cement, silica fume, fine aggregates (sand) conforming to ASTM C33 gradation, tap water, and steel fibers. Cement and sand properties are shown in Table II and the properties of silica fume and steel fibers in Table III. The formulated mix design for this investigation is

illustrated in Table IV. It predominantly uses materials that are readily available locally to reduce the production cost. Through preliminary testing, it was determined that this specific mix design yields an average compressive strength of about 50 MPa in 28 days as well as a modulus of rupture of 19 MPa. For the ECC preparation, the dry ingredients, excluding the steel fibers, were initially blended in a mechanical mixer for two minutes as per [32]. The steel fibers were then introduced and blended uniformly with the dry mix, see Figure 1. Following the even distribution of the fibers, water was systematically added and mixed for an additional 2 min. After achieving the appropriate consistency, ECC was cast into plate molds with dimensions of 375×75×25 mm, as in [32]. The samples were de-molded after 24 hr and cured in a water bath for 28 days at 20 ± 2 °C.

TABLE II. PROPERTIES OF CEMENT AND SAND

Cement									
Chemical composition %	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	K ₂ O	SO ₃	IR	L.O.I
Result	60.72	20.22	4.41	5.03	3.72	0.34	2.19	0.97	2.4
Physical properties	Specific gravity	Fineness (m ² /kg)	Setting (min.)		Compressive strength (MPa)				
			Initial	Final	3 days		7 days		
Result	3.17	326	110	270	21		34		
Sand									
Physical properties	Specific gravity (bulk)					Absorption, %			
Results	2.63					1.08			
Gradation, sieve size (mm)	9.5	4.75	2.36	1.18	0.6	0.3	0.15		
% passing	100	96	84	68	45	16	3		

TABLE III. PROPERTIES OF SILICA FUME AND STEEL FIBERS

Silica Fume				
Physical properties	Color	Specific gravity	Fineness (m ² /kg)	
Results	Grey	2.27	Min15000	
Steel fiber				
Physical properties	Average length (mm)	Average diameter (mm)	Density (kg/m ³)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Results	13	0.3	7864	2860

TABLE IV. MIX DESIGN OF ECC

Material	Cement	Sand	Silica fume	Water	Steel fibers
Content (kg/m ³)	900	1000	100	400	2% by volume

B. Asphalt Concrete

The raw materials selected to prepare the asphalt concrete mix for this research included the asphalt cement that was procured from the Doura oil refinery, situated in the southwestern part of Baghdad. The latter underwent tests based on the Superpave performance grade requirements (Figure 3). The results, detailed in Table V, verify that the asphalt cement aligns with the PG 64-16 grade requirements. The aggregate used for this experimental study was crushed quartz, sourced from the Amanat Baghdad asphalt concrete mix plant in the northern region of Baghdad. The aggregate coarse and fine fractions were separated utilizing sieves. They were later recombined in the right ratios to align with the grading criteria for a mix of wearing course type IIIA, depending on SCRB/R9 specification [33]. The aggregate physical properties are presented in Table VI. Figure 2 illustrates the aggregate

gradation curve. The mineral filler employed is ordinary Portland cement, sourced from a cement factory in Kubaissa (west of Iraq), as shown in Table VII. In this study, Kevlar Aramid fiber was employed as a geotextile to strengthen asphalt concrete, as shown in Table VIII. The geotextile was cut into 400×300 mm strips, matching the size of the asphalt concrete slab samples. It was positioned in two specific locations: at the specimen base and at 1/3 depth from the base. To promote bonding between the geotextile and the asphalt concrete, and to maintain consistent asphalt cement in the mix, the geotextile strip was pre-coated with a liquid asphalt layer (tack coat) prior to its insertion into the specimen.

Fig. 1. Blending the ECC contents with a mechanical mixer.

TABLE V. ASPHALT CEMENT PROPERTIES

Asphalt cement	Properties	Designation	Measured temperature (°C)	Measured parameters	Specification requirements [34]
Original	Flash Point (°C)		-	292	230 °C, min
	Viscosity at 135 °C (Pa.s)	AASHTO T316	-	0.454	3 Pa.s, max
	DSR, G/sinδ at 10 rad/s (kPa)	AASHTO T315	58	3.3108	1.00 kPa, min
			70	0.946	
RTFO Aged	Mass Loss (%)	AASHTO T240	-	0.708	1%, max
	DSR, G/sinδ at 10 rad/s (kPa)	AASHTO T315	58	4.0337	2.2 kPa, min
			64	3.1667	
			70	2.0774	
PAV Aged	DSR, G.sinδ at 10 rad/s (kPa)		28	4394	5000 kPa, max
			25	6371	
	BBR, Creep Stiffness (MPa)	AASHTO T313	-6	119.8	300 MPa, max

TABLE VI. AGGREGATE PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Test	ASTM standard	Result	Specification requirements [33]
Coarse Aggregate			
Apparent specific gravity	C127	2.652	-
Bulk specific gravity		2.631	-
Water absorption (%)		0.287	-
Soundness (sodium sulfate solution loss) (%)	C88	3.5	12 max.
Wear percentage (Los Angeles abrasion) (%)	C131	18	30 max.
Flat and elongated (5:1) (%)	D4791	3	10 max.
Fractured pieces (%)	D5821	92	90 min.
Fine Aggregate			
Apparent specific gravity	C128	2.611	-
Bulk specific gravity		2.537	-
Water absorption (%)		0.902	-
Clay lump and friable particles (%)	C142	1.21	3 max.
Sand equivalent (%)	D2419	58	45 min.

TABLE VII. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF MINERAL FILLER

Test	Results
Specific gravity	3.17
Passing sieve No.200 (%)	98

TABLE VIII. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF GEOTEXTILE

Product Type	Aramid woven fabric
Style/Pattern	Unidirectional twill
Material	Phenylene terephthalamide polymer
Thickness	1 mm
Color	Yellow
Tensile strength (gpd)	24
Density (kg/m ³)	1451

Fig. 2. Aggregate gradation curve for wearing course.

Fig. 3. Asphalt cement tests.

C. Asphalt Concrete Mix Design

The mix design for asphalt concrete specimens was carried out using the Marshall method [35]. Each specimen was prepared by compacting 75 blows on each side via an automatic Marshall compactor. The Optimum Asphalt Content (OAC) is determined as the average of the three asphalt content values that yield the highest stability, maximum density, and 4% air void content, as outlined in AI's manual series No. 2 [36].

Fig. 4. Mix design results of asphalt concrete with the Marshall method.

Five different asphalt cement percentages were tried, starting at 4% by weight of the total mix and increased by 0.5 percent increments, resulting in tests at 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, and

6%. Figure 4 presents the results for stability, flow, density, and volumetric properties, like AV% and VMA%. The optimal asphalt content was determined as 5.0% by weight of the total mix. At this content, both the flow value and VMA% met the set standards: 2 to 4 mm for flow and over 14% for VMA.

D. Preparation of Asphalt Concrete Mix

During the specimen preparation, the aggregate was separated using sieves of certain sizes: 19, 12.5, 9.5, 4.75, 2.36, 0.3, 0.075 mm and a pan as shown in Figure 1. The aggregate was combined in a preparation bowl and weighed based on the intended specimen shape and test type. The mixed aggregate was blended uniformly for two minutes and heated at 150 °C for 2 hr. The bowl was subsequently weighed and a predetermined quantity of asphalt cement, preheated to a range of 150–155 °C (aligning with a binder viscosity of 170 ± 20 c.St), was added in the mixture. The bowl content was thoroughly mixed on a hot plate for 2 min. To achieve a consistent compaction temperature, the bowl was then placed in an oven for 10 min at 140 °C. Meanwhile, the mold was preheated at 100 °C. The material was then transferred to the mold and compacted as per test specifications, using a Marshall compactor for cylindrical specimens and a roller compactor for slab specimens. The roller compaction was performed in five progressive phases with varying forces, ranging from 0.5 kN to 4 kN. Different loading cycles were applied in each phase. The compaction was ended once the sample density matched the predetermined Marshall density. For the Marshall Test, the sample weight was 1150 gm, while for the slab specimen, later trimmed for prisms for the OT test, the weight was 13340 gm. In the case where the geotextile was integrated at a depth of one-third from the specimen base, a two-phase compaction approach was implemented. At the beginning, a third of the total mix weight was introduced into the mold, undergoing the initial compaction phase with a force of 0.5 kN across 5 loading cycles. After this initial compaction, the geotextile was laid on top of the already compacted portion. The remaining two-thirds of the mix were then added to the mold and the compaction continued accordingly. Subsequently, the slab specimen was trimmed using a rock cutter to achieve the required dimensions of 375×75× 50 mm.

E. Overlay Test (OT) Procedure

The OT evaluates the susceptibility of asphalt mixtures to reflection cracking and explores the potential of ECC as an interlayer system as well as geotextile fabric in mitigating reflection cracking. In this test, each specimen type was replicated three times to ensure the accuracy and consistency of the results. In the case of the ECC interlayer usage, the asphalt concrete prism is bonded to the ECC prism with a dimension of 375×75 mm employing different heights of ECC: 7 mm, 12 mm, and 17 mm. When geotextile at the bottom of asphalt concrete prisms was used, the geotextile was tacked to the bottom of asphalt concrete prisms utilizing liquid asphalt (tack coat). For a more realistic field representation, the asphalt sample either strengthened or unstrengthened, is bonded to two Portland Cement Concrete (PCC) prisms, each 75 mm wide and 50 mm high, applying epoxy glue. These PCC prisms serve as a base, representing the concrete pavement beneath typical asphalt overlays in practical conditions. The complete setup

was then attached to two horizontal steel platforms of an overlay testing apparatus separated by a gap of 5 mm, which imitates the width of joints or cracks in actual overlaid roads. To facilitate optimal bonding, a sustained weight of 10 kg was positioned atop the asphalt concrete layer for 60 min. The sample setup is exhibited in Figure 5.

Conforming to ASTM WK26816 guidelines [37], the test was conducted under displacement control mode, utilizing one cycle every 10 s. The sliding platform moves in a cyclic triangular waveform, consistently reaching a maximum shift of 0.635 mm (0.025 inches) at a testing temperature of 20 °C. The key result of the OT is the number of load cycles to failure (Nf). Authors in [39] illustrated that failure is initiated when the peak load in a cycle decreases to 93% below the highest initial load [38, 40-42]. Another two parameters that can be extracted from this test are the critical fracture energy (G_c) and the Crack Progression Rate (CPR). Figure 6 displays the cycles of the implemented displacement, load, and their related time sequences. Furthermore, Figure 6 illustrates the variation in the peak tensile load as related to the number of loading cycles and the typical first hysteresis loop. Subsequently, G_c is calculated using the equation $G_c=W/A$, where W encapsulates the area under the load-tension curve (from zero load to maximum tension load) and A represents the specimen cross-sectional area (width \times height). G_c represents the energy required to initiate a crack at the bottom plane of the specimen during the initial loading phase. A higher G_c suggests that the asphalt mix requires more energy to initiate the crack, indicating enhanced resistance to the onset of reflection cracking. In contrast, CPR demonstrates the specimen crack resistance during the propagation phase. It is derived from fitting a power equation to the curve that represents the decrease in load with the increasing number of loading cycles, where the power term b in the fitted equation is consistently negative. For practical considerations, the absolute value of b is termed as the CPR. A higher CPR denotes accelerated crack propagation within the asphalt specimen, which may result in a shorter lifespan for the asphalt concrete.

Fig. 5. Overlay test setup.

Fig. 6. Typical output for OT.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Effect of ECC on Reflection Cracking

Figure 7(a) presents the discernible enhancement in the G_c values, a measure of the energy required to initiate a crack as the thickness of the ECC interlayer increases. When compared to the Reference Specimen (RS), which exhibits a G_c value of 0.5701 kJ/mm², there is a marked improvement in the ECC samples. The ECC7 displays an approximately 78% increase in G_c , while ECC12 and ECC17 manifest 185% and 269% boost, respectively. This amplification in G_c suggests that asphalt mixes integrated with thicker ECC interlayers show superior resistance to the reflection cracking inception, signifying their potential efficacy in infrastructure longevity. Concurrently, the declining trend in CPR values, evidenced in Figure 7(b), confirms that once a crack is formed, its spread is remarkably slower in ECC-integrated specimens as opposed to the RS. Starting with the RS, a CPR of 0.361 is observed, setting a benchmark for subsequent evaluations. With the introduction of ECC7, the CPR sharply drops to 0.174, marking an approximate 52% reduction. The trend of diminishing CPR continues with ECC12, registering a value of 0.132, which translates to a further decrease of around 24% compared to ECC7. The peak of resistance is achieved with the ECC17 mix, which has the lowest CPR of 0.081. This value designates a reduction of nearly 78% compared to the RS.

Fig. 7. Effect of ECC on different reflection cracking parameters. (a) G_c , (b) CPR, (c) max tensile load, (d) Nf.

With differing ECC interlayer thicknesses, Figure 7(c) provides a clear visual representation of the maximum tensile load capacities of various asphalt mixes. The maximum tensile load is a critical parameter as it determines the ultimate force a material can withstand before significant deformation or failure

occurs, indicating the material toughness. In examining the RS, it displays a tensile load capacity of 2528.4 N. Introducing ECC into the mix exhibits a notable increase in this capacity. The ECC7, for instance, holds a load of 3230 N, marking an increase of about 27.8% relative to the RS. A thicker ECC interlayer, ECC 12, shows an even higher load capacity, resulting in a maximum load of 5345 N corresponding to an improvement of 111.5% compared to the RS. The peak load is reached with ECC17, which sustains a staggering load of 7638 N resulting in a gain of over 202% compared to the reference specimen RS. The presented trend suggests that the incorporation of thicker ECC interlayers substantially amplifies the tensile strength of the asphalt concrete overlay. This enhancement is paramount for overlaid pavement that endures daily mechanical stresses, emphasizing ECC's potential to reduce the likelihood of early damage.

The results of Nf, as presented in Figure 7(d), agree with those obtained from the other reflection cracking parameters, showcasing a consistent pattern of performance enhancement. Significant improvements are visible with the use of ECC interlayers when compared to the RS, with an Nf value of 294. The ECC7 registers an Nf value of 1824, marking a noticeable improvement of approximately 520% compared to RS. ECC12 showcases an Nf of 2674, equating to an enhancement of around 810% over the RS. This upward trend peaks with ECC17, which commands an Nf value of 3845, signaling an extraordinary enhancement of roughly 1307% in relation to the RS.

Based on the data presented, it is evident that the use of ECC interlayers substantially ameliorates resistance to reflection cracking. The progressive improvements observed across varying ECC thicknesses highlight its pivotal role in ensuring superior performance and durability in pavement overlay applications

B. Effect of Geotextile on Reflection Cracking

Reviewing the G_c values presented in Figure 8(a), a clear enhancement is observed with the geotextile incorporation. The RS specimen displays a baseline G_c value of 0.5701 kJ/mm². When the geotextile is placed at the bottom (GB), the G_c value shows an increase to 0.8305 kJ/mm², marking a 45.7% improvement. Positioning the geotextile at 1/3 depth from the bottom (G1/3) yields a G_c value of 0.9821 kJ/mm², denoting a 72.3% enhancement from the RS. This suggests that geotextile placement, particularly at 1/3 depth, can contribute significantly to the energy required to initiate the crack. For the CPR outcomes, the RS stands at 0.361. However, with the GB incorporation, a slight reduction to 0.321 is observed, translated to an 11.1% improvement. A more pronounced decrease is evident with G1/3, which displays a CPR of 0.194, representing a 46.3% improvement. Such figures indicate the reduced crack propagation risk with geotextile placement, especially at 1/3 depth, as shown in Figure 8(b).

When considering the maximum tensile load a specimen can endure, it is imperative to note the inherent potential and improvements associated with the use of geotextile materials. As shown in Figure 8(c), the RS yields a maximum tensile load of about 2528.4 N.

Fig. 8. Effect of geotextile on different reflection cracking parameters. (a) G_c , (b) CPR, (c) max tensile load, (d) Nf.

Introducing geotextile at the bottom (GB) brings forth a transformative change. The load measurement surges to 3273.2 N, marking an increase of 744.8 N, i.e. an appreciable 29.5% improvement in comparison with the RS. This increment is indicative of the added tensile strength and robustness incorporated due to the geotextile placement at the base. However, shifting the geotextile to 1/3 depth from the bottom

(G1/3) advances the tensile load even further. This results in a maximum load of 3675 N, an increase of 146.8 N from GB and a substantial 1146.6 N leap from RS. This difference places the G1/3 improvement at a significant 45.4% over the RS. Not only does such a figure emphasize the structural fortification provided by geotextile, but also underlines the noticeable advantage of its placement at 1/3 depth.

The results regarding the Nf parameter are exhibited in Figure 8(d). The RS establishes the baseline with an Nf value of 294. This fundamental figure offers a perspective on the endurance and lifespan of a typical specimen when subjected to repeated stresses. With GB incorporation, the Nf shows a discernible increase, reaching an Nf of 445. This elevation, accounting for 151 from the RS, signifies a commendable 51.4% enhancement. The trend of improvement rises with the G1/3. The Nf ascends to 754, marking a spike of 309 from GB and a substantial 460 from the base RS. This denotes an outstanding 156.5% amplification over the RS. Such pronounced increments underscore the extended service life and reinforced resilience against cyclical loadings offered by geotextiles, especially when located at 1/3 depth.

As a result, the findings obtained highlight the pivotal role that geotextile installation plays in enhancing the ability of asphalt specimens to resist reflection cracking. The consistent outperformance of the G1/3 configuration accentuates the potential benefits of geotextile positioning in extending infrastructure durability and lifespan.

C. Performance Comparison of ECC and Geotextile

Figure 9 shows the performance related to reflection cracking of specimens strengthened using an ECC interlayer of varied thicknesses compared with those reinforced with geotextile at different positions. This Figure also presents the key parameters including G_c , CPR, maximum tensile load at the first loading cycle, and Nf.

The results shown in Figure 9(a) clearly illustrate that overlays reinforced with ECC, particularly ECC17, typically exhibit higher average G_c values when compared to the reference specimen and overlays reinforced with geotextile. This is indicative of their augmented ability to resist fracture, suggesting they can endure more stress before the onset of cracking. The improvement rate in the G_c value for ECC17 was found to be 153%, 96%, and 22% in relation to GB, ECC12, and ECC7 specimens, respectively. Based on [39], a G_c threshold of 0.5 differentiates a soft mix (below 0.5 N.mm/mm²) and a tough mix (0.5 N.mm/mm² or more). The mixes with high toughness offer excellent resistance to the onset of reflection cracking. Based on Figure 9(a), the ECC specimens generally perform better than those with geotextiles. Furthermore, specimens reinforced with geotextile at 1/3 the depth from the bottom of the asphalt concrete specimen perform better than those with geotextile at the bottom.

Specimens ECC12 and ECC17 notably exhibit lower CPR values. This suggests a slower rate of crack development compared to the GB and G1/3 specimens. The inherent characteristics of ECC likely contribute to this behavior, offering increased resistance to crack progression, thereby potentially extending the asphalt overlay service life. In a direct

comparison with the GB and G1/3 specimens, ECC17 exhibited a CPR reduction of 75%, while ECC12 showed a 59% reduction. Using the criteria set in [39], where a CPR value of 0.5 differentiates between materials resistant to cracking (≤ 0.5) and those more vulnerable (> 0.5), mixes strengthened by ECC clearly outperform GB and G1/3, while G1/3 demonstrates better crack resistance than GB.

Fig. 9. The parameters for reflection cracking for ECC and Geotextile specimens. (a) Fracture energy (Gc) and crack propagation rate (CPR), (b) maximum tensile load and Nf.

According to the maximum tensile load values shown in Figure 9(b), a clear trend emerges when examining the impact of ECC reinforcement. ECC12 yields an impressive increase of 63% in the maximum tensile load, emphasizing its notable capability to withstand tension during the initial loading cycle. Meanwhile, ECC17 stands out with a remarkable enhancement of 134% in tensile strength. This underscores the essential role that the amount of ECC plays in augmenting the overlay tensile resilience. Among the variants, ECC17 is the clear standout. Conversely, ECC7 demonstrates only a marginal improvement when compared to the reference specimen. In the context of the GB and G1/3 specimens, GB displays a slightly better tensile performance than G1/3.

The number of load cycles to failure (Nf) for different mix types exhibited in Figure 9(b), underscores the superior performance of ECC-strength mixtures when contrasted with the specimen reinforced with GB. ECC7 showcases a significant improvement, presenting an increase of approximately 310% over GB. This enhancement becomes even more pronounced with ECC12, which offers a growth of about 501%. The peak performance is reached with ECC17, marking a staggering rise of roughly 764% compared to GB. In

the geotextile category, while G1/3 surpasses GB with a growth of approximately 69%, it does not come close to the performance metrics set by the ECC mixtures. In summary, ECC variants, especially ECC17, illustrate a decisive advantage in reflection cracking resistance over GB, and although G1/3 is superior to GB, it lags significantly behind the ECC mixtures in terms of percentage increase for Nf.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the test results obtained in this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Overlays strengthened with ECC, particularly ECC17, display a higher resistance to reflection cracking compared to the reference specimen (RS). Their higher average Gc values indicate a better ability to resist fracture compared to both RS and specimens reinforced with geotextile.
- In comparison to the RS, ECC specimens in general fare better against reflection cracking. Within the geotextile placements, specimens positioned at 1/3 depth from the bottom outperformed those placed directly at the bottom.
- Crack Propagation Rate (CPR) findings revealed that ECC12 and ECC17 possess a superior capacity to decelerate crack development. Specifically, ECC17 recorded a 75% reduction, and ECC12 reported a 59% reduction in CPR, distinguishing them as more resilient than the GB and G1/3 specimens.
- In the context of tensile strength, ECC17 exhibited a 134% augmentation, underscoring the pivotal role of ECC in boosting tensile resilience in overlays. On the contrary, ECC7 showed a marginal enhancement compared to the RS.
- ECC mixtures, with ECC17 in particular, demonstrated a pronounced advantage in the number of load cycles to failure (Nf) over the GB specimen. With ECC17 recording a significant surge of roughly 764% compared to GB, its dominance is evident.
- Although the G1/3 variant reinforced with geotextile surpassed the GB in performance parameters, it notably trailed the ECC-enhanced mixtures, especially when considering the percentage surge for Nf. The Nf for the average of ECC specimens is larger than the average Nf of the geotextiles specimens by 463%.

Since the results are limited to the available materials and testing programs, future research is recommended to explore cost optimization strategies for different ECC thicknesses. Additionally, considering alternative fibers in ECC mixes is advised. It is essential to validate the experimental findings using field-based trial sections.

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A Human Face Detector for Big Data Analysis of Pilgrim Flow Rates in Hajj and Umrah

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital world, some crowded venues still rely on outdated methods, such as counting people using counters or sensors at the entrance. These techniques generally fail in areas where people move randomly. Crowd management is an important challenge for ensuring human safety. This paper focuses on developing a crowd management system for Hajj and Umrah duty. Motivated by the recent artificial intelligence techniques and the availability of large-scale data, a crowd management system was established and is presented in this paper. Utilizing the most recent Deep Learning techniques, the proposed crowd management system will be charged with detecting human faces, face identification, tracking, and human face counting tasks. Face counting and detection will be achieved by computing the number of people in a given area. Face detection and tracking will be carried out for person identification, flow rate estimation, and security. The suggested crowd management system is composed of three key components: (1) face detection, (2) assignment of a specific identifier (ID) to each detected face, (3) each detected face will be compared to the stored faces in the dataset. If the detected face is identified, it will be assigned to its ID, or a new ID will be assigned. The crowd management system has been developed to improve the Cross-Stage Partial Network (CSPNet) with attention module integration. An attention module was employed to address object location challenges and a channel-wise attention module for determining the objects of focus. Extensive experiments on the WIDER FACE dataset proved the robustness of the proposed face detection module, which allows for building reliable crowd management and flow rate estimation systems through detecting, tracking, and counting human faces. The reported results demonstrated the power of the proposed method while achieving high detection performance in terms of processing speed and detection accuracy.

Keywords-crowd management; face counting; face tracking; deep learning; attention module; channel-wise module; Hajj; Umrah

I. INTRODUCTION

Hajj and Umrah are considered the pillars that each Muslim hopes to perform at least once in life. All Muslims travel to Mecca and Madinah to perform the Hajj and Umrah rituals, which form some of the most populous human gatherings as millions of persons share the same place simultaneously. The Saudi government works to guarantee greater safety and to develop new crowd management techniques to maintain security for pilgrims when they perform their religious duties. Hajj and Umrah present a significant concern for the kingdom as it expects to receive more than 30 million Hajj and Umrah performers by 2030. An efficient crowd management system is essential to control place access and the departure from them and to reduce crowds from congested spots. In this way, the system certifies higher safety and security for the attendants when performing their religious duties. As a very high number of persons per-place are expected, an efficient crowd management system is essential for fast management and flow rate estimation. A reliable crowd management system will be designed using Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems for face detection, tracking, and counting. Human face detection and counting are employed in a crowd management system to quantify the number of people in a given area, whereas face recognition is used for security and health concerns. The main purpose of building a new effective crowd management system is to ensure a safer and more comfortable way for persons to move around overcrowded places. Generally, the system will be charged with the control of people's entry and exit to manipulate crowd flow. The developed system ensures the detection of dangerous situations and can call for specific teams' intervention to address these problems.

In Hajj and Umrah, people move continuously, affecting crowd management accuracy. To address this issue, an additional face detection part was introduced for the crowd management system to identify individuals by personal identifying IDs and to track them in overcrowded places. By adding a face recognition framework, we ensure the entry of authorized people to the crowded area and avoid multiple counts of persons contributing to more precise statistics. The two critical components of the suggested crowd control system are data processing and the identification storage framework. First, data collected from cameras are processed for human face detection and identification. In the data storage module, the identified faces will be stored in the dataset for further face recognition and to avoid multiple counting of the same faces.

Deep Learning (DL)-based techniques present a wide range of applications, including indoor object detection and recognition [1-4], wayfinding assistance navigation [5], license plate detection [6], traffic sign detection [7], logo recognition [8], face recognition [9], and pedestrian detection [10].

Channel-wise attention and spatial attention mechanisms are utilized in DL architectures, particularly in Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to enhance the ability to focus on important features and regions within an input. Channel-wise attention allows the network to assign different weights to each channel of the input feature map. This is beneficial when certain channels capture more relevant information for a given

task. The model can learn to emphasize important channels while suppressing less informative ones. Channel-wise attention helps the network capture complex relationships between channels, facilitating the learning of non-linear combinations of features. This can be particularly useful in tasks where understanding inter-channel dependencies is crucial. Spatial attention mechanisms enable the model to focus on specific spatial regions within the input feature map. This is valuable when certain parts of the input contain more relevant information for the task at hand. The network can learn to attend discriminative regions. Such spatial attention can reduce the computational cost by focusing on informative regions, allowing the model to allocate resources more efficiently. This is especially important in scenarios where computational resources are limited, such as in real-time applications. Motivated by the power of DL models and the benefits of attention mechanisms, the present work proposes a crowd management system with a face detection framework based on the Cross-Stage Partial Network CSPNet [11]. Enhanced by attention modules, this system ensures an optimized module with high detection accuracy and processing speed. We used attention modules to enable the network to focus better on the target. CSPNet is proposed to reduce the computational cost and the network memory storage without decreasing the network accuracy. By employing the CSPNet, we ensure real-time processing with low computational complexity on low-end devices. To improve accuracy and reduce false-positive predictions, channel-wise and spatial attention modules were applied to the CSPNet at the backbone and prediction stages. The WIDER FACE [12] dataset was used to train and test the suggested model. This dataset provides various challenging conditions, including occlusion, pose variation, varying light conditions, and geometric deformations. The most significant part of the dataset has been collected from overcrowded areas. This makes our work very efficient and effective as it is trained in challenging conditions.

II. RELATED WORK

Various works have been proposed in the literature to address the problem of crowd management and control. Authors in [13] proposed a new simulation approach for real-life crowd management based on DL algorithms. The system can identify the crowd level into five main categories. The developed system comprises two main parts: one for crowd-level classification and the second for constituting the color of warning. Crowd monitoring presents an extensively researched topic as it is primarily related to public safety. This topic is highly challenging as it addresses problems such as occlusion, pose estimation, and density variation. In [14], the authors reviewed the crowd management works by presenting the latest developments and performances obtained in crowd management and control using machine learning techniques.

Most crowd management systems still rely on old methods, such as engaging persons to count at places' entrance. However, these methods fail in crowded places where the movement is random and variable. In [15], the authors introduce the use of Deep Convolutional Neural Networks (DCNNs). The system implementation has been performed employing NVIDIA Graphic Processing Unit (GPU) to

parallelize the process and obtain near-real-time results. Authors in [16] proposed a crowd management system based on image classification and an alarm module. The image classification module relies on using CNNs. In [17], a new crowd management system was suggested dealing with high-level architecture with decision support. Authors in [18] review and summarize the strengths and applications of crowd management systems in different crowd scenarios. Authors in [19] introduced a new efficient DL model called deep Uran Event. The model is built utilizing Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs).

The world urbanization prospects in its 2018 revision estimate that 68% of the world population will have been living in urban spaces by 2050. Such an increase in the urbanization flow poses significant pressure on the city and space infrastructures. This fact poses serious problems and a crowd management system would be beneficial in tackling some of those issues. Using many sensors and cameras with limited human intervention to analyze videos, results in developing new effective crowd-monitoring systems. In [20], the authors discuss building an intelligent crowd management system applying condition capabilities. For intelligent systems, detecting and predicting abnormal crowd behavior has emerged as a challenging task in building efficient crowd control systems. In [21], the authors propose a new approach that exploits the psychological state and cognition to detect nine crowd behaviors. The developed approach is based on two cognitive DL-based frameworks with a psychological fuzzy computation framework.

Real-time crowd control and analysis present an active research area within the computer vision and AI community. Various methods for crowd management have been proposed to be implemented for different applications, such as people

counting [22], disaster management [23], and event management [24]. Although various works have been suggested to address the problem of crowd management and control, few of them fit real-time conditions. As it is still a challenging matter to be solved, authors in [25] reviewed the currently available crowd management analysis techniques.

III. THE PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed pipeline followed in this work to build the crowd management system is presented in Figure 1. A camera will capture and collect data from the surrounding environment as a system input. The system will then be charged by conducting face detection, and it will later focus solely on the face cropping in the input data. The saved data will be then compared with each cropped face. If matched faces exist, they will be assigned to their identifier (ID). If not, a new identifier will be assigned to the cropped face. Finally, the cropped face identifiers will be stored in the dataset for further face identification and tracking. The face detection task is highly challenging due to different factors, including lighting, small face sizes, occlusion, different viewpoints, geometrical deformations, etc. So, to overcome all these issues, it is critical to design a robust crowd management system. We propose to build a crowd management system based on a Cross-Stage Partial Network (CSPNet) and two powerful attention blocks. A spatial attention module to address object location challenges and a channel-wise attention module for determining the objects of focus were employed. We note that the applied techniques enhanced the system detection performance and processing speed. Generally, DCNNs require substantial computational resources and high-end devices for application implementations. CSPNet was introduced to resolve this problem as it provides a lightweight architecture that can contribute to real-time applications using mobile devices.

Fig. 1. Proposed crowd management system

CSPNet introduces an optimized version of DenseNet [26]. The basic architecture of DenseNet is based on stages. Every stage contains a dense block containing K dense layers. The DenseNet mechanism is described by:

$$x_1 = W_1 * x_0$$

$$x_2 = W_2 * [x_0, x_1]$$

$$x_K = W_K * [x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{K-1}] \quad (1)$$

where $*$ means a convolution operator, $[x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{K-1}]$ means a concatenation of x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{K-1} , W_i is the weight of each layer, and x_i is the output of the i^{th} dense layer. To reduce the error between the network output and the target output, the DCNN

uses backpropagation techniques to update the network weights. Weight updating in the DenseNet architecture is computed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_1' &= f(w_1, g_0) \\
 W_2' &= f(w_2, g_0, g_1) \\
 W_3' &= f(w_3, g_0, g_1, g_2) \\
 &\vdots \\
 W_K' &= f(w_K, g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{K-1})
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

where f is the function of weight updating, g_i is the gradient propagation to the i^{th} dense layer.

This approach will produce various dense layers that will repeatedly learn duplicated gradient information. This task presents an issue as it increases the network computational cost. A cross-stage partial network is introduced to limit the computational requirements. CSPNet ensures a richer gradient combination while keeping low computational costs. It achieves this by dividing the gradient to follow different network paths. CSPNet employs cross-stage partial DenseNet as a network backbone. As mentioned in Figure 2, the base layer feature map is split into two paths: $[x_0', x_0'']$. A deep concatenation of x_0', x_0'' results in the x_0 original feature map. The transition layer output x_T will be a function of the dense layer $[x_0'', x_1', \dots, x_k]$. x_T will be processed with x_0 and undergo another transition layer to result in x_U . The feed-

forward pass can be computed with (3) and the weight updating of the cross-stage partial DenseNet is computed in (4).

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_k &= W_k * [x_0'', x_1, \dots, x_{k-1}] \\
 x_T &= W_T * [x_0'', x_1, \dots, x_k] \\
 x_U &= W_U * [x_0, x_T]
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_k' &= f(W_k, g_0'', g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{k-1}) \\
 W_T' &= f(W_T, g_0'', g_1, g_2, \dots, g_k) \\
 W_U' &= f(W_U, g_0', g_T)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

The CSPDenseNet architecture is presented in Figure 2. It generally reuses the original DenseNet characteristics while avoiding multiple gradient information reuses by dividing the gradient into two paths. The main advantages of splitting the feature map are the following:

- It doubles the gradient paths during backpropagation, which makes it deal with the gradient vanishing problem.
- Deeper depth of the feature map at the base layer whereas the division of the feature map reduces considerably the computation cost.

In our work, the CSPDenseNet architecture fusion was employed first: the merge is performed first, then the transition. As a network for object detection, CSPNet uses an Exact Fusion Model (EFM), as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 2. CSPDenseNet Architecture.

Fig. 3. EFM architecture for object detection. Blue rectangles represent pyramid feature maps. The green arrows represent the fusion of feature maps at different levels.

To detect and localize objects, CSPNet architecture introduces the use of EFM, which captures the most relevant components in a Field of View (FoV) for each anchor. This method is especially employed for aggregating the feature pyramid. This technique is based on assigning each ground truth object with just one prior bounding box. Only one anchor box that surpasses the IOU threshold refers to a ground truth object. Generally, the anchor box is the same size as a grid cell's FoV view. The corresponding bounding box for the i^{th} scale is lower by the $(i-1)^{\text{th}}$ scale and upper bounded by the $(i+1)^{\text{th}}$ scale. So, the EFM mind is to assemble the most relevant features from three different scales. To minimize the amount of computation complexity and memory cost, CSPNet introduces the max-out techniques. These techniques are utilized to compress the feature maps and address these problems. An attention module was proposed to enhance the model's focus on human faces and ensure greater effectiveness for the detection process. The channel-wise module is presented to address the issue of what to focus on, while the spatial attention module is utilized to address the issue of where to focus. In the proposed work, a combination of the two modules was used for better performance. Attention modules are designed using pooling layers. However, we propose designing an attention module based on fully convolution layers in this work. We note that by replacing pooling by convolution layers [27], we ensure better learning capabilities of the model. Figure 4 depicts the architecture of the spatial attention module.

The 1×1 convolution layer has been used as a squeezing unit. Also, it prevents the backpropagation influence directly on the backbone. The 3×3 convolution layer is utilized as a 3×3 excitation unit followed by an 1×1 convolution. These are the main components of the spatial attention mechanism. The spatial attention map's relative location and receptive field are the same as the backbone output. In the proposed work, the spatial attention module was integrated in a plug-in manner into the backbone architecture. The second attention module applied in our work is the channel-wise attention module. Figure 5 illustrates the designed channel-wise attention module.

Fig. 4. Spatial attention module architecture.

Fig. 5. Channel-wise attention module.

The utilization of distinct pooling layers is critical for the attention process. Using a global average pooling layer allows for object expansion, but using a max-pooling layer assures object location identification. Also, we provide improved identification of small items by employing global max pooling rather than max pooling.

In the current work, human face detection was solved at different aspect ratios to achieve more efficient results. However, only mixed max pooling and global average pooling were adopted for building channel-wise attention. The main novelty in the proposed work is the design of an additional domain attention network to the pooling structure. Three main rules must be respected in the design of the attention domain network: The network must be data-driven, possibly adapting the intermediate feature map and outputs to the input. Also, the network should be powerful to weigh the raw vectors. Finally, the network must be lightweight to reduce the computation complexity. A hidden layer and three fully connected layers are the main components of the proposed domain attention network. We should mention that the suggested attention module was included to keep the network structure and benefit from the pre-trained weights. The spatial module was integrated into the dense layers, while the channel-wise module was integrated into the dense layers after the spatial module application. As the top layers present high semantic information with low spatial features, applying the channel-wise module at this stage was very critical.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Experimental Environment and Evaluation

In this work, we develop a robust crowd management system highly recommended in overcrowded areas, especially during Hajj and Umrah duty. Training and testing experiments have been performed using the WIDER FACE dataset [12], which provides various challenging conditions. All the data were manually annotated and collected from overcrowded events, which match the studied task. All the experiments conducted in this work were carried out on a desktop with an i7 CPU, 32 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA GTX 960 GPU. The DL framework Pytorch with CUDA support and the CUDNN library for processing acceleration were used to perform the proposed experiments. The Open Computer Vision (OpenCV) library was employed for image display and manipulation. The DCNN was trained for 40 epochs. We utilized 0.001 as an initial learning rate and ADAM as the network optimizer. The algorithm is used to optimize the gradient descent variant and accelerate the convergence process. Training and testing image sizes were fixed to 320×320 pixels to achieve real-time performance. The batch size was 4. Loss optimization provides information on how well the training is. If training goes well, the loss will converge to a worthy minimum. The loss optimization curve of the proposed model for classification and localization is presented in Figure 6. To evaluate the proposed work, mean Average Precision (mAP), processing speed, and model size were considered. To study the effectiveness of the integrated improvements applied to the original CSPNet, the original and the improved version of CSPNet were evaluated on the same dataset. Table I provides the obtained results.

Fig. 6. Loss optimization of the proposed model for classification (class_loss) and localization (box_loss).

TABLE I. OBTAINED PERFORMANCE OF THE PROPOSED AND THE ORIGINAL CSPNET VERSION

Model	mAP (%)	Speed (FPS)	Model size (MB)
CSPNet (original)	91.25	19	216.7
CSPNet (ours)	93.36	18	227.3

We note that by applying the integration of the attention module, the network detection accuracy was improved. To further study the efficiency and robustness of the proposed work, a comparison with the state-of-the-art works in terms of detection accuracy and speed was proposed. Based on the obtained results, our work outperforms previous works and achieves a satisfactory trade-off between detection precision and speed. Table II provides a comparison with the state-of-the-art techniques.

TABLE II. COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART

Model	mAP (%)	Speed (FPS)
Faster RCNN [28]	88.7	4
[29]	89.1	10
HOANG [30]	75.4	12
CSPNet (ours)	93.36	18

As mentioned in Table II, the proposed crowd management system achieved reliable detection results which outperform those obtained by the other methods regarding both detection and processing time. The output of the face detection algorithm is illustrated in Figure 7. The proposed algorithm presents a high detection rate even for tiny and occluded faces.

B. Ablation Study

An ablation study was conducted to show the impact of different attention modules. The spatial and channel-wise attention modules were adopted to enhance the model's performance in detecting small targets. Table III summarizes the achieved results with different configurations compared to

the original model. The spatial attention module greatly improves the detection accuracy with only 0.69% and does not affect the inference speed. The channel-wise attention provides a favorable improvement of 1.32% in detection accuracy, while a slight decrease in inference speed was presented. In the case of adopting both attention modules, an enhancement of 2.11%

was achieved with a decrease of only one FPS in inference speed. Both attention modules require 10.6 MB of additional memory. The achieved improvement proved the efficiency of the proposed attention module for enhancing the detection accuracy without degrading the inference speed and without a considerable increase in computation complexity.

Fig. 7. Demo of the face detection algorithm.

TABLE III. ABLATION STUDY ON THE ATTENTION MODULES

Model	mAP (%)	Speed (FPS)	Model size (MB)
CSPNet (original)	91.25	19	216.7
CSPNet with spatial attention	91.94	18.7	220.5
CSPNet with channel-wise attention	92.57	18.4	223.2
CSPNet with both attentions	93.36	18	227.3

V. CONCLUSION

Managing large crowds during Hajj and Umrah remains a formidable challenge. The most effective solution for handling crowded spaces involves the development of crowd management systems utilizing human face detection, as opposed to the entire body, due to its efficiency and time-saving benefits. This study introduces an innovative crowd management system that leverages CSPNet with a DenseNet backbone. To enhance the system, attention modules were incorporated, including a spatial attention module to address object location challenges and a channel-wise attention module for determining the objects of focus. Extensive experiments have showcased the system's efficiency, demonstrating superior results in terms of both detection accuracy and speed when compared to state-of-the-art approaches. The significance of using CSPNet with attention mechanisms extends to its practical implementation in real-world crowd management applications. The robustness, adaptability, and high performance demonstrated by the system make it a promising candidate for deployment in settings such as large events,

public spaces, and religious gatherings. It is important to note that the proposed system requires high-performance devices for optimal functionality. In future endeavors, the proposed approach will be implemented in a real-world application and evaluated under genuine conditions.

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Experimental Investigation of Polymer and Nanomaterial modified Asphalt Binder

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ABSTRACT

Modifying the asphalt binder and mixture becomes one of the best ways to mitigate pavement distress and increase the service life of constructed road networks. This study aimed to evaluate the influence of modified asphalt binders with the best different percentages of polymer and nanoparticles. Typical asphalt binder (penetration, softening point, and viscosity) and frequency sweep tests were used to evaluate the physical and rheological properties of modified asphalt binders with 5% Acrylonitrile Styrene Acrylate (ASA), 5% aluminum oxide nanoparticles (Al_2O_3), and 5% calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). The results showed that the physical properties of all modified blends improved compared to those of the base asphalt binder. The improvement in softening point was up to 19%, the penetration reduction was nearly 69%, and the sensitivity to elevated temperatures was reduced by up to 13%. Evaluation of the rheological properties showed that modified asphalt with 5% Al_2O_3 binder had the highest permanent deformation resistance, followed by 5% ASA. The 5% CaCO_3 binder showed a small improvement compared to the other samples. The results showed that the 5% Al_2O_3 binder had the highest complex modulus and the lowest phase angle, which means that it has the best viscoelastic properties. Therefore, it can be recognized as the best asphalt binder among the modified binders in this study.

Keywords-modified asphalt binder; acrylate styrene acrylonitrile; polymer; physical and rheological properties; nanoparticles

I. INTRODUCTION

Asphalt pavement is used in motorways and urban streets due to its convenience, ease of maintenance, wear resistance, and fast traffic setting time. Asphalt concrete has become the most common pavement surface worldwide [1]. Classic surface road pavement is commonly a component of asphalt, which is a flexible black adhesive hydrocarbon material, mineral aggregate, and filler materials. These elements are more likely to work together to resist road deformation [2]. Many roads around the world are influenced by challenging environmental conditions, aging issues, and increased load traffic, which results in cracks and ruts [3-4]. Numerous studies have been conducted to investigate the appropriate additive materials to improve pavement performance. In [5], the characteristics of modified asphalt binder with calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) and aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles were investigated at

elevated temperatures, showing excellent compatibility and higher storage stability. The stiffness of the modified binders improved with an additional increase in the modifier rate, reaching up to 5% in terms of rheological properties and indicating better resistance to permanent deformation. In [6], polymer/nanocomposite-modified asphalt binders were shown to be significantly improved compared to the base asphalt binder. In [7], the effects of carbon nanofibers on performance-modified asphalt with liquid epoxidized natural rubber were evaluated, showing an increase in stiffness and a reduction in temperature susceptibility. The addition of carbon nanofibers significantly increased the bonding properties between the base and rubberized binders. The optimal content of the modifiers was found to be 0.4% with 6% LENR. Using high percentages (7-8%) of Styrene-Butadiene-Styrene (SBS) polymer to modify the asphalt binder results in superior performance compared to a lower amount of polymer (3%) [7].

In [8], the influence of the nanomaterial-modified asphalt binder and basalt fiber was investigated, showing that the modification of the asphalt binder can mitigate permanent deformation and rutting. In [9], modified asphalt with SBS nanomaterials showed an improvement in compatibility between SBS and asphalt mixtures, using rheological and physical property tests, increasing the storage stability of modified asphalt binders. The mechanical characteristics of modified asphalt binders are mainly affected by the properties of pure bitumen, the modifier, the blending condition, and the interaction of the modifier with bitumen [10]. Asphalt binders are often modified to improve one of the fundamental asphalt attributes, such as stiffness, elasticity, fragility, and strain resistance, but also resistance to cumulative devastation [11]. Polymers are one of the most commonly modified asphalt materials. The addition of polymers to bitumen binders improves both physical and rheological properties, and various studies have shown that it improves the viscoelastic characteristics of the binder by broadening the temperature range resulting in increased resistance to thermal stress and rutting [12-13]. Polymer-modified asphalt mixes can improve the bonding of binder aggregate particles, improving the durability of the pavement. Polymers generally contribute 3.0% to 7.0% of the sample weight [12]. A variety of polymers have been effectively integrated with bitumen concrete engineering, which can be classified into two categories, namely elastomers and thermoplastic elastomers [14-15]. Thermoplastic elastomers have the potential to offer sufficient tension strength when they are subjected to high levels of strain. Researchers have prioritized their investigation over elastomers due to their ability to return to their original shape after stretching. SBS is a common thermoplastic elastomer that is compatible with asphalt [16]. Common types of elastomers that are highlighted to improve the high-temperature capability of asphalt are Ethylene Vinyl Acetate (EVA), Polypropylene (PP), and Polyethylene (PE) [17]. Although blended polymers with asphalt concrete play an important role in improving the physical and rheological properties of asphalt, several studies have observed a significant flaw in the modifying process. The additive polymer must be compatible enough with bitumen concrete to form a homogenous combination and eliminate the separation issue during storage, delivery, and implementation. Furthermore, insufficient aging tolerance is a challenge related to polymer-modified asphalt [18-19].

This study aims to evaluate the effects of modified asphalt binders with different percentages of polymers and nanoparticles, focusing on the performance comparison of the best percentages of modifiers.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

The unmodified asphalt binder used had a 60/70 penetration grade as a reference. One binder was modified with polymer, namely, 5% ASA, and the other two binders were modified with nanoparticles, namely 5% Al_2O_3 and 5% CaCO_3 . The modified asphalt binders were produced in the laboratory using polymers and nanoparticles. The ASA polymers, nano Al_2O_3 and CaCO_3 were in powder form. Table I shows the physical properties of the examined asphalt binders.

TABLE I. PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF BASE AND MODIFIED ASPHALT BINDERS

Material	Properties	Unit	Value
Asphalt 60/70	Specific gravity	-	1.03
	Penetration @ 25°C	0.1 mm	70
	Softening point	°C	47
	Viscosity @ 135°C	(Pa.s)	≤ 3
	Ductility @ 25 C	mm	≤100
	Powder form	-	-
ASA	Size	mm	2
	Powder form	-	-
Al_2O_3	Size	nm	13
	Powder form	-	-
CaCO_3	Size	nm	40
	Powder form	-	-

B. Sample Preparation

The samples of ASA, Al_2O_3 , and CaCO_3 were prepared using the melt method. The modifiers were added and blended with the base asphalt binder using a Silverson high shear mixer at a speed of 5000 rpm and at 170 °C for 1.5 hr to produce homogenous mixtures [5, 20-21].

III. RESULTS DISCUSSION

A. Effect of the Modifier on the Penetration of Binders

Figure 1 depicts the penetration values of the different binders. The unmodified binder had the highest penetration value of 70 dmm followed by CaCO_3 , and Al_2O_3 binders with values of 40 and 25.45 dmm, respectively. In addition, the 5% ASA binder had the lowest penetration value. These results indicate that the binder modified with ASA is stiffer than others, due to the particle uniform distribution of the polymer compared with nanoparticles that face agglomeration due to particle size [5].

Fig. 1. Penetration test of unmodified and modified binders.

B. Effects of the Modifier on the Softening Point of Binders

The softening point is used to determine the temperature at which a phase change occurs in the binder under standardized conditions. A high softening point indicates low temperature susceptibility and vice versa. Figure 2 shows that the base binder had the lowest softening point temperature at 47°C and the modified binders had relatively higher. The 5% ASA binder

had the highest softening point temperature (56 °C), followed by the 5% CaCO₃ binder at 54°C, while the 5% Al₂O₃ binder had the lowest (53°C), which was still better than base asphalt. The modified binders generally had better resistance to rutting. The 5% ASA binder had the greatest tendency to resist deformation at intermediate to high temperatures.

Fig. 2. Softening point of unmodified and modified binders.

C. Viscosity

Viscosity is the binder's resistance to flow during the contraction period. Figure 3 shows a reduction in viscosity with increasing test temperatures, as the mixture slowly moves from the solid to the liquid state. At a predetermined temperature on the viscosity/temperature scale, the viscosity of the modified binders was higher compared to the unmodified binder for most parts of the test, indicating that the modified binders had better performance at high temperatures. This indicates how workable the binder will be. All viscosity values were within the limitations of the Superpave, as they were less than 3 Pa.s.

Fig. 3. Viscosities of base and modified asphalt binders.

D. Storage Stability

A binder has good storage stability properties if the difference in the softening point temperatures between the lower and upper test sections is less than or equal to 2.5 °C. Figure 4 shows that all the binders examined had a temperature

difference of less than 2.5 °C. Therefore, it is evident that all the binders will exhibit good compatibility, good workability properties, and stable storage during high temperatures. Moreover, nanoparticles have more compatibility with the binder compared to the polymer, which might be due to the particle size of the nanomaterials.

Fig. 4. Storage stability of base and modified binders.

E. Effect of Modifiers on Rheological Properties of Binders (Isochronal Plot of Complex Modulus and Phase Angle)

The isochronal plot can be used to determine the viscoelastic properties of the different binders when evaluated over a set of temperature ranges at a specific frequency. The isochronal plots of the complex modulus in Figure 5 were created using the complex modulus (G^*) and the temperature (°C) at a reference frequency of 1.592 Hz. As expected, there was a general reduction in the G^* value for all the corresponding binders with an increase in test temperature. All the G^* values of the modified binders superseded those of the base binder. In incremental order, the binder containing 5% CaCO₃ performed better than the base binder, followed by the binders with 5% ASA and 5% Al₂O₃. The 5% Al₂O₃ binder had the highest G^* values, indicating that it has the greatest tendency to resist the applied stresses acting on it before failure. This means that when used in the construction of asphalt pavements, it will exhibit better resistance to rutting compared to the other binders.

The phase angle is the time lag between the applied stress and the corresponding strain. This curve is particularly helpful in understanding the viscoelastic properties of the binder and also indicates the mechanical loss. In a perfectly elastic body, there is no time delay (zero) when there is an applied load, but a highly viscous binder will have a large phase angle value approaching 90 °C. Figure 6 shows the phase angle of the binders tested. The base binder had the greatest time delay when subjected to stress, indicating its low elasticity. Although the different binders had some degree of elasticity when subjected to stresses, the binder with 5% Al₂O₃ had the lowest phase angle values, which is an indication that it is the most elastic among the binders tested.

Fig. 5. Isochronal plot of complex modulus A for the binders.

Fig. 6. Isochronal plots of phase angle at 1.5 Hz for the binders.

F. Rheological Master Curve

The master curves for the different binders were constructed to establish the relationship between the complex modulus and the reduced frequencies under multiple temperatures and times. A reference temperature was adopted to construct the master curve, while adjustments were made to other temperatures to achieve a single continuous smooth curve. This curve can be used to predict the binder stiffness and its properties at any given temperature. Figure 7 shows the master curves for asphalt binders examined. The base binder had the lowest complex modulus to reduced log ratio. In descending order, the 5% CaCO₃ binder performed better but was less to the base in resisting stresses than the 5% Al₂O₃ and 5% ASA binders, respectively. The binder with 5% Al₂O₃ had the greatest tendency to resist permanent deformation.

G. Rutting Parameter

To determine the rutting characteristics of the base and modified asphalt binders, the $G^*/\sin(\delta)$ was plotted at temperatures of 45, 55, 65, and 75 °C as specified by the Strategic Highway Research Program (SHRP). Figure 8 shows that the lowest value of $G^*/\sin(\delta)$ was recorded by the base binder, followed by 5% CaCO₃. Although the $G^*/\sin(\delta)$ values

recorded for the 5% ASA and the 5% Al₂O₃ binders were closely matched, the latter had the highest value closely followed by the former. The binder containing 5% Al₂O₃ has the greatest ability to resist permanent deformation and the greatest toughness at high temperatures. All modified binders had a $G^*/\sin(\delta)$ exceeding 1000 Pa at 70 °C. Furthermore, the high values obtained for the complex shear modulus of the nanomodified binders indicated their ability to absorb large stresses by dissipating applied forces during high and intermediate temperatures, thereby providing good rutting and fatigue resistance.

Fig. 7. Complex modulus master curve for base and modified binders.

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on the rutting parameter of base and modified asphalt binders.

H. Fatigue Parameter

To determine the fatigue parameter of bitumen at intermediate temperatures, the Superpave stipulates a maximum value of 5000 kPa described by the formula $G^*\sin(\delta)$. This demonstrates the better performance of the modifiers in resisting fatigue at intermediate temperatures. Figure 9 shows that at 35 °C, the base and the 5% CaCO₃ binders failed to meet the required minimum.

Fig. 9. Effect of temperature on fatigue parameter of base and modified asphalt binders.

I. Failure Temperature

According to the SuperPave specifications, the failure temperature of an asphalt binder is the point where the value of $G^*/\sin(\delta)$ falls below 1000 Pa. These are the criteria adopted in determining the performance grade of asphalt binders [22]. The results in Figure 10 indicate that the lowest failure temperatures were recorded by the base binder followed by the 5% CaCO₃ with temperatures of 69 and 74 °C, respectively, which indicates that they are more sensitive to temperature. The other modified binders, namely 5% ASA and 5% Al₂O₃, had higher failure temperatures of 77 and 78 °C, respectively, and showed less sensitivity when compared to the base asphalt.

Fig. 10. Failure temperatures of unmodified and modified binders.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study compared three commonly used binder modifiers, ASA, Al₂O₃, and CaCO₃, with the base binder. Concerning the physical properties of the binder, it has been shown that, in general, polymers and nanomaterials decrease the penetration of bitumen binders, which, on the other hand,

leads to higher softening points and viscosity values. The results of the storage stability tests showed that all modified binders maintained a stable form after storage at high temperatures. When considering the rheological effects, properties such as rutting resistance at high temperatures, cracking resistance at low temperatures, and performance improved massively when introducing these modifiers. From the rutting values obtained, it is evident that the binder with 5% Al₂O₃ nanoparticles had the highest ability to resist permanent deformation and the highest toughness at high temperatures. The 5% ASA polymer binder exhibited the greatest strength under thermal cracking from the isochronal plot. The 5% ASA and 5% Al₂O₃ binders had higher failure temperatures compared to the base asphalt and 5% CaCO₃ binders. The use of polymers and nanomaterials has proven to be very important in the performance and durability of asphalt pavements by modifying the physical and rheological properties of the binders. Utilizing nanomaterials has proven to yield better properties when used as a modifier in asphalt binders, but their use is limited due to their uniquely complex production and subsequent use in experimental research.

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Cooperative Spectrum Sensing Performance Assessment using Machine Learning in Cognitive Radio Sensor Networks

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ABSTRACT

The Cognitive Radio (CR) is an imminent technology, intended to make more effective use of the available spectrum by giving access to licensed frequency bands by unlicensed Secondary Users (SUs) without affecting Primary licensed Users (PUs). Depending on the region where the energy is being observed, each CR communicates local decisions or the seen energy to the Fusion Center (FC). This study presents the many plots that discuss an enhanced double threshold through the Cooperative Spectrum Sensing (CSS) approach. The FC then combines local decisions with the measured energy values to reach a final decision. The usage of several machine learning methods in spectrum decision with the myopic decision is estimated. The system seeks to enhance the long-term overall performance of the SU.

Keywords-cognitive radio; energy detection; GMM; support vector machine; double threshold; Smith-Waterman algorithm; spectrum sensing

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's demand for wireless communication services is increasing explosively with the advancement of wireless communication technology and the development of the global economy. Cognitive Radio (CR) has been suggested to cope with the problem of spectrum sparsity due to the ineffective use of spectrum resources [1-2]. For example, CR technology allows Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) to dynamically access frequency bands with improved propagation characteristics, such as the Ultra-High Frequency (UHF) bands used for television broadcasting. A spectral gap in the UHF band, also known as the TV void, can be used to operate this CR-based WSN. The lower the frequency in this band is, the greater are the transmission range and power efficiency. The

association of CR technology with WSNs has led to the Cognitive Radio Sensor Network (CRSN) paradigm.

Fixed threshold techniques are comparatively easy to implement but are prone to making erroneous decisions due to the variability of the noise signal. This impact in higher false-alarm and false-positive rates. False alarms refer to situations where a noise signal is incorrectly identified as the primary signal. Additionally, false alarms can be more precisely defined as the result of false positives. As a result, this leads to underutilization of spectrum resources as transmission opportunities are lost. False detection can also occur when the primary signal is misidentification for a noise signal. [3-4]. It is a highly unwanted state as it leads to an interruption of the primary user's transmissions. Error detection is also a false negative. When the decision threshold is fixed at a static level

on top of the noise floor, the Fixed Threshold Technique (FTT) runs into another issue. A weak primary signal goes undetected below the threshold and secondary transmissions can cause harmful interference to primary users. Additionally, some FTT techniques require empirical analysis of spectral measurement data, making the threshold selection process very difficult to automate [5]. This is very impractical, especially for CRSNs where nodes must be fully autonomous without human intervention. Additionally, it is not always possible to have a priori knowledge of the noise variance and spectrum. Therefore, adaptive and autonomous thresholding methods are preferred for CRSN applications. This article proposes a new CSS scheme using Machine Learning (ML) techniques. Generally, the ML techniques are used for pattern classification. ML divides patterns into distinct classes by using feature vectors that are extracted from the patterns and are fed as input into a classifier [6]. In CSS, we treat the feature vector as an "energy vector," whose components are the estimated energy levels of each CR device. Depending on the kind of the learning approach used, classification algorithms can be either unsupervised learning, such as Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) and K-means clustering or supervised, such as State Vector Machines (SVMs) and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN).

II. BACKGROUND WORK

The proposed CSS scheme uses the quantized energy levels to train a classifier and the acquisition report to calculate distance, thus determining the class label of the current acquisition report. This is different from the spectrum acquisition technique [7]. Instead of majority voting, we opted to utilize the approach of SWA, an efficient distance measurement algorithm, to compute the harmony between the present capture report and the training report. Based on thresholds determined by various fusion rules, authors in [8] proposed various classification schemes. This article uses different fusion rules in the fusion center. It considers the weight of distinct CR users before making a global decision. Focus is given on finding thresholds for various schemes, where KNN is used as the classification scheme. Also, the fusion rule of the proposed method basically uses the distance between training and test reports at the CR user level, while Fusion Center (FC) considers the historical veracity of each CR user. Therefore, FC's global fusion rules use each CR user's training reports and performance history. Global merge rules are therefore more robust and reliable.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

To estimate the probability density of the input for the given N input vectors in \mathcal{R}^d and M linear combination of basic functions we have:

$$P(x) = \sum_{j=1}^M p(x/j) p(j) \quad (1)$$

where $P(x)$ is the x^{th} density point, $p(x/j)$ is the j^{th} density component, and mixing coefficients are denoted by $p(j)$ which is the earlier likelihood that a data vector was created from the j^{th} mixing component.

A. Main Property

We consider M is large enough and the model's parameters are properly adjusted. We will just talk about the situation of a mixture of Gaussians:

$$p(x/j) = \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma_j^2)^{d/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\|x - \mu_j\|^2}{2\sigma_j^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

B. Training

The maximum likelihood technique will be used to evaluate the parameters of the mixture model $p(j)$, μ_j , and σ_j :

$$E = -\ln L = -\sum_{n=1}^N \ln P(x^n) - \sum_{n=1}^N \ln \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^M p(x^n/j) p(j) \right\} \quad (3)$$

When E is minimal, maximum likelihood L is achieved. The analytical solution (using Bayes theorem and Gaussian definition) is:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial \mu_j} = \sum_{n=1}^N p(j/x^n) \frac{\mu_j - x^n}{\sigma_j^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial \sigma_j} = \sum_{n=1}^N p(j/x^n) \left\{ \frac{d}{\sigma_j} - \frac{\|x^n - \mu_j\|^2}{\sigma_j^3} \right\} = 0 \quad (5)$$

By the definition of the mixing coefficients as the "SoftMax function" (also called Gibbs distribution or normalized exponential), we have:

$$p(j) = \frac{\exp(\gamma_j)}{\sum_{k=1}^M \exp(\gamma_k)} \quad (\forall j \gamma_j \geq 0) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial \gamma_j} = -\sum_{n=1}^N p(j/x^n) - p(j) = 0$$

This system model leads to the following solution:

$$\hat{\mu}_j = \frac{\sum p(j/x^n) x^n}{\sum p(j/x^n)} \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\sigma}_j^2 = \frac{1}{d} \frac{\sum p(j/x^n) \|x^n - \hat{\mu}_j\|^2}{\sum p(j/x^n)} \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{p}(j) = \frac{1}{N} \sum p(j/x^n) \quad (9)$$

To find the values of these interdependent parameters, standard nonlinear optimization must be used. Another practical solution is the algorithm of Expectation-Maximization (EM):

1. Estimate initial values
2. Calculate new values
3. Back to step one, until convergence

A local minimum is reached by the EM algorithm. It is helpful in a variety of circumstances in addition to the one just mentioned. As an example, let us assume that $L(\mu, \sigma)$ represents the likelihood as a function of deviation σ and standard expectation μ . Under certain convexity assumptions, we can maximize L by repetitively estimating, determining, and freezing. Figure 1 shows the proposed CSS framework. Majorly, it consists of two modules, namely classification module and training module, both working independently.

Fig. 1. The suggested CSS framework's structure.

When the classification module wants to determine the availability of a channel, the CRN constructs the test energy vector and provides it to it. The classification module resolves the channel availability using the classifier on the basis of the test energy vector. Finding a channel's availability in the CR network often takes just a few seconds. Due to their minimal complexity, the proposed CSS approaches' classification delays can satisfy these criteria [9]. The training module is important for providing the trained classifier in the classification module, as well as the training energy samples used to train the classifier. When the CRN first opens and when there are changes in the radio environment, the training module can be activated (for example, when the configuration of the PU network changes).

IV. THE PROPOSED CSS FRAMEWORK WITH ML TECHNIQUES

An enhanced adaptive double threshold scheme in energy detection that reduces the collision probability between PU and SU and improves spectrum utilization by reducing the false alarm probability is proposed [10]. This technique involves deciding the absence or presence of the PU using sub thresholds inside the uncertain region, between two thresholds. The uncertain region is the confused region, where no decision has taken about the availability of the PU. Repeated sensing is necessary, which increases the spectrum sensing cycles and hence the detection performance, which degrades. A suitable threshold determination procedure is employed in this module to reduce the spectrum sensing cycles and obtain better detection performance. Under a noise uncertainty environment, the thresholds determined in the above procedure are made

adaptive based on the minimum and maximum noise variances to overcome noise uncertainty [11]. Furthermore, cooperative spectrum detection in CRN is expected to improve detection efficiency even in environments with fading and receiver uncertainty. A modified two-stage energy detector is used for local decision-making, while global decision-making is done by the coordinator. The proposed two-stage energy detection scheme alleviates the problem of spectral detection failure by using a single threshold in the first stage and an adaptive double threshold in the second stage. The performance of the improved two-stage energy detection scheme in cooperative spectrum acquisition is analyzed in terms of detection probability, error probability, and acquisition time.

CSS [12-13] is proposed to overcome node failure and fading problems. Each SU informs the FC of a local decision. The results of each CR are then combined by the FC using specific fusion rules H . The majority of the rules are OR and AND rules. The detection probability (Q_d) and false alarm probability (Q_f) of the OR rule linkage scheme are given in [14] as:

$$Q_d = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^M (1 - P_{di}) \tag{10}$$

$$Q_f = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^M (1 - P_{fi}) \tag{11}$$

where P_{fi} and P_{di} are the false alarm and detection probabilities of the i^{th} SU and M is the number of CR's participating in the CSS.

Fig. 2. CSS.

In conventional energy detectors each CR will makes local decisions based on a single threshold. The premise H_1 is correct if either the computed energy (X) or the measured energy (O) is higher than a certain threshold, otherwise the hypothesis H_0 stands. In the case of a double threshold energy detection approach, if the observed energy X is larger than 2, hypothesis H_1 holds true. If it is less than one, hypothesis H_0 holds true. No decision is made and CR will return to acknowledgment if the detected energy X falls between the two thresholds, i.e. $\lambda_1 < X < \lambda_2$. The threshold λ can be calculated by:

$$\lambda = Q^{-1}(P_{fa}) \sqrt{2N\sigma_w^4 + N\sigma_w^2} \tag{12}$$

Additionally, thresholds λ_1 and λ_2 are given by:

$$\lambda_1 = (1 - p) \lambda \tag{13}$$

$$\lambda_2 = (1 + p) \lambda \tag{14}$$

ML is typically used to achieve a solution to an optimization problem close to the optimal one, when the

problem is too complex for conventional optimality analysis and it is unknown how to map the input data to the output (the answer to the problem). This kind of uncertainty in wireless communication systems results from noise (thermal, color, impulse, etc.) or other sorts of channel distortion or interference. In this article, we apply ML as a means of improving good sensing. ML-based detection techniques aim to detect frequency channel availability by developing the process as a classification problem. A classifier must determine its two states (empty or occupied) for each frequency channel, supervised or unsupervised. To determine channel availability, these classifiers make use of information like probability vectors and energy statistics.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

Simulation research was conducted to assess the effectiveness of the ML energy detection method and the simulation results were used for evaluation. The classification error rate of the classifier is shown in Table I. The best weights obtained for SVM, KNN, and NB classifiers are 0.8873, 0.8691, and 0.2804 respectively. This shows that the SVM classifier has the most impact whereas the NB classifier has the least. Additionally, the outcomes demonstrate that the ensemble classifier minimizes the class 1 error as well as the overall error to 2.81%, thus reducing system risk [15]. Figure 3 shows the theoretical and simulation ROC (Q_d vs. Q_{fa} curves) performances for N=500 and 1000.

TABLE I. CLASSIFICATION ERROR RATE (%)

Classification methods	Total error rate	Channel unavailability class error rate
KNN	13.901	43.902
NB	14.347	28.206
SVM	12.182	85.365
Proposed	5.625	12.00

Fig. 3. Q_d vs Q_{fa} for a single energy detector.

Figure 4 shows the single-threshold and double-threshold ROCs (Q_d vs. Q_{fa} curves) at SNR = -5 dB for 200 samples. For this reason, the confusion area is not considered. For simplicity, we simulated that every CR used the same threshold λ and $\rho = 0.1$.

Fig. 4. Q_d versus Q_{fa} for a single energy detector.

Fig. 5. Q_d versus Q_{fa} for a single energy detector.

We assumed $M = 5$ as the number of SUs involved in collaboration. Figure 5 clearly shows the advantages of the expected scheme over traditional CSS. The curve is drawn at SNR -8 dB with 100 samples. The proposed approach raises the detection probability for $Q_{fa} = 0.1$ by almost 10%.

Fig. 6. P_e SNR (in dB).

Figure 6 shows the output waveform between the probability of decision error (P_e) and SNR by setting $P_{fa}=0.1$. It can be seen that the suggested technique minimizes the decision error in the low SNR range. Figure 7 shows the graph between P_e versus PU and SU positions. It can be seen that the designed scheme minimizes the decision error in the low SNR range.

Fig. 7. PU and SU positions.

VI. CONCLUSION

CSS is an intelligent collaborative acquisition method. It has high measurement accuracy, is self-adaptive to the environment, and is more complex to operate than traditional joint measurement methods. The designed system learns from the situation the true state of the PU. The total error rates of KNN, NB, and SVM classifiers are 13.901, 14.347, and 12.182. Our proposed method reduced this metric to 5.625 and the channel unavailability class error rate (43.902, 28.206, 85.365) was also reduced to 12.00. Hence, the proposed system is able to make more effective use of the available spectrum, while seeking to enhance the long-term overall performance of the SUs.

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Presenting the Secure Collapsible Makerspace with Biometric Authentication

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ABSTRACT

Traditional product design learning is inefficient, costly, and limited by safety concerns in physical and smaller-scale school workshops. The Secure Collapsible Makerspace is a mobile makerspace with smart sensors and an expandable work area facility. This study aims to develop a smart mobile makerspace platform using edge computing architecture and the biometric security model to compare real-time learners' engagement time and design performance. The developed platform consists of four blocks that provide service as a makerspace for the learners and monitor their utilization in a secure environment. The edge computing architecture allows real-time analysis of the users' makerspace utilization. A total of 750 learners were accessed for their product design outcome which presented a positive correlation of 0.72 between the engagement time and the design assessment with a corresponding p-value less than 0.001. This study concludes that makerspaces can be a platform that improves students' performance in hands-on activity-related learning.

Keywords-active learning; biometrics; Internet of things; intrusion detection; remote monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Combinations of robotics and Internet of Things (IoT) advancement provide excellent engineered systems that can be applied for monitoring and ensuring the security of autonomous learning platforms [1-2]. This study presents the Secure Collapsible Makerspace for remote learning monitoring. The proposed makerspace is an advanced, low-cost robot with a centralized and distributed security system equipped with time monitoring facilities. The robustness of the design makes this robot ideal for learning centers with limited space. The collapsible feature with centralized security control provides the robot with flexibility in offering wider learning options in STEM.

STEM learning is nowadays becoming costly and takes plenty of resources and manpower [3-4]. Efforts have been taken by the learning centers to improve knowledge delivery effectiveness through self-learning and automated monitoring systems [5-6]. Many such systems are currently software-based, limiting the learners' hands-on experience, especially in product design [7]. Traditional product design learning which operates in extensive physical workshops is highly inefficient in space management and costly. The existing smaller-scale workshops also proved ineffective in schools as learners are not allowed to be in the workshop without the supervision of the teachers or lab instructors to ensure the safety and security of the workshop and its equipment [8].

The role of mobility in learning became more crucial during the post-COVID-19 pandemic era which has created a knowledge gap in technology for product design learning [9-10]. Most learning centers are left behind in terms of infrastructure and equipment. The mobility aspect of the Secure Collapsible Makerspace is expected to close this gap by providing a powerful learning experience. Mobility in learning allows an individual to move away from his or her everyday context, such as the classroom, to take the experience of learning to the next step [11]. This approach is expected to be effective in addressing the knowledge gap in product design-related courses with a minimum investment.

Product design is a combination of different learning dimensions such as computer-aided 3D design sketching, product manufacturing, digital designing, and others [12]. As such, the learning process requires much more individual time and attention beyond formal classroom learning. In the traditional learning modality, the home has been a conducive environment for learners to practice beyond the formal classroom. Parents have played an important role in assessing or monitoring their children's engagement in extended learning. Nowadays, urbanization has created limited space in most homes, especially in high-rise living environments. This created a new need for a reliable learning monitoring system. As such, the design of the Secure Collapsible Makerspace embedded with biometrics security features serves a dual purpose by offering a secure working platform as well as usage monitoring.

The current study introduces a novel solution called the Secure Collapsible Makerspace, an advanced robot with integrated security systems. It addresses several pressing issues in STEM and product design education: the high cost and resource demands that hinder accessibility for diverse learners, the limited practical experience caused by software-based monitoring systems, the inefficient use of physical workshop space, and the amplified knowledge gap brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, it recognizes the changing dynamics of home learning environments due to space limitations. This innovative approach aims to provide an affordable, flexible, and secure learning platform, bridging these educational gaps.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. A Framework of Biometrics Security-driven IoT Edge Learning Monitoring

Edge computing can be used to improve the performance, reliability, and security of applications that rely on real-time data processing and analysis. A unique capacity of IoT edge is connecting to both private and public networks such as the Internet with less than 1 ms latency capacity. The connecting device includes smart devices capable of processing data from mobile phones and basic surrounding sensors including security and usage time monitoring. The IoT edge computing data capturing method is selected considering its capacity to collect and process data at the edge of the network close to the data. This offers several advantages over traditional cloud-based IoT systems including lower latency, reduced bandwidth requirements, and improved data security. In this study, the

edge computing capacity is applied to monitor learners' engagement time. Previous research has shown that monitoring equipment usage in skill-based learning can provide educators with the learners' competency level of achievement without the physical monitoring that is required in traditional skill-based learning assessment [13]. The designed platform features a dual-function security system that can ensure the safety of the platform while also recording user engagement time. A biometric sensor is integrated with electric linear actuators enabled by fingerprint data that optimize the platform performance, reduce energy consumption, and ensure safety. The operational capacity is further enhanced with an algorithm that can accurately control the mechanical movement of the platform based on the data received from the biometric system. The hardware is made of lightweight wooden panels and electric linear actuators embedded with a closed-loop control system with limit sensors that provide high-accuracy control and positioning with flexible processes and low operating costs.

The learning environment usage time monitoring technique refers to methods of tracking and analyzing the utilization of tools and resources among learners during their learning. This technique can provide valuable insight into learners' behavior and engagement, as well as inform instructional design and improve learning outcomes. There are various types of techniques and tools used for monitoring [14]. This study adapted learning engagement time tracking using a biometric fingerprint device and other forms of summative assessment to provide a comprehensive view of learners' learning engagement. The biometric fingerprint device was selected over other types of monitoring devices such as surveillance cameras and face recognition scanners, considering the cost sustainability factor in maintaining the system in remote locations as well as its reliability over a long period.

B. Hardware Modeling

The conventional laboratory is typically classified based on the subject matter, such as physics, chemistry, and computer laboratory. These laboratories are further divided into various types based on the learners' learning levels, resulting in up to four to five different types of laboratories in the school. This setting requires additional manpower for laboratory operation and maintenance which eventually increases cost. These well-equipped laboratories are often underutilized due to access security and time restrictions. This study offers a solution for the issue by proposing a mobile and collapsible platform driven by an IoT security model. To effectively utilize an interdisciplinary learning environment such as product design, a more robust laboratory is required. The Secure Collapsible Makerspace is designed to address a robust requirement of recent Industry 4.0 technology. Figure 1 illustrates a 3D model of the Secure Collapsible Makerspace modeled using the Sketchup 3D design and modeling software [15]. The user authentication module with two-factor authentication based on biometric technology provides access to authorized personnel such as teachers to activate the platform. The user access data are captured and sent to the edge through built-in Wi-Fi to reduce response time. Multiple heavy-duty wheels are installed to enable the physical mobility of the platform in serving the

needs of different groups and locations. The portable front and side door panels are scalable to meet the learning environment setting for the product design course.

Fig. 1. 3D model of the proposed platform.

Figure 2 illustrates the expanded Secure Collapsible Makerspace. The platform is equipped with three collapsible tables which can be activated individually by the learners according to their needs. A fixed table equipped with six power outlets in addition to two power outlets at the back panel is rated at 240 V AC to hold the electrical equipment. To effectively control the expansion of the panels and the lifting of the tables, an automated actuator model is designed using biometric activation that commands a microcontroller to perform the panel activation operation.

Fig. 2. 3D model of the expanded platform.

The platform is also designed with compartments for books and component drawers, added with storage for foldable chairs. It is powered by a domestic voltage supply of 240 V AC supported by an extended power cable to cater to the movable nature of the platform. Considering the safety of the users and the platform, a turn-to-release emergency stop pushbutton is installed to halt the panel operation in the event of an emergency. The other safety aspect of the platform expansion

is the appropriate selection of the actuator which will be discussed in the next section.

C. Automation Configuration

The two-factor biometric-based authentication is applied to provide more secure control by providing feedback and comparing the fingerprint input from the user and the passcode with the existing records. Three failed attempts in a row within five minutes will lock the platform for 20 minutes as a security measure. Upon successful verification, the system will initiate the panel movement sequence. An array of limit sensors is used as a feedback mechanism to stop the individual panel's motion at the predetermined limit for safety measures. The same motion control mechanism is used in activating the learners' tables. Figure 3 shows the block diagram of the Secure Collapsible Makerspace control mechanism.

Fig. 3. Platform control mechanism.

D. Security Access Model

The platform access control is built on a two-factor authentication security access model that uses biometric fingerprint data with a passcode to identify and authenticate individuals attempting to gain access to the platform and its resources. Table I describes some key characteristics of the commonly used biometric security system [16-19]. According to Table I, the fingerprint biometric security model is the most optimal option in terms of usability, scalability, and cost. Since the purpose of the user authentication module is to allow authorized personnel to access the platform with fingerprint and passcode, the fingerprint images of registered users along with user ID and passcode are stored locally and backed up in the cloud storage. The system can be reset if there is a security breach or data corruption by restoring the factory settings from the cloud backup system.

User authentication based on the biometric technology approach is used during the activation of both the platform and tables for users. Minimizing the False Acceptance Rate (FAR) and False Rejection Rate (FRR) is a challenge for fingerprint biometric systems in multi-user and multi-level access settings. The system must be able to accurately distinguish between authorized and unauthorized users while minimizing false positives and false negatives. Error detection is caused by several factors, including the finger surface condition and the positioning of the finger. To address this issue, the authentication module is configured to capture images from any two fingers and two impressions per finger for memory optimization [20]. The proposed approach is expected to overcome the sensor's specific requirements on fingerprint images, which can limit flexibility and interoperability with other systems.

TABLE I. BIOMETRICS DATA CHARACTERISTICS

Characteristics	Fingerprint	Hand geometry	Iris	Facial	Voice
Ease of use	High	High	Medium	Medium	High
Accuracy	High	High	Very high	High	Medium
Verify time	< 3 s	3 s	< 5 s	3 s	5 s
Error incidence	Dryness, dirt, deep injury, age	Hand surface injury, age	Poor lighting, positioning	Lighting, glasses/ lens, hair	External noise, user health conditions
Security	High	Medium	Very high	Medium	Medium
Long term stability	High	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
Device user interface	Optical scanner	Hi-resolution camera	Illumination IR scanner	Hi-resolution camera	Hi-quality microphone
User age group suitability	Stable from 12-45 y.o. age	Stable from 21 y.o. age	Stable from 30 y.o. age	Affected by aging	Affected by aging

Collecting and storing biometric data raises concerns about privacy and security. While passwords can be changed, biometric data are unique to a user and may be permanently compromised if stolen or lost [21]. The biometric data of this platform are governed by a three-level security authorization by two different individuals to prevent data breaches or misuse. Another issue is system scalability, which requires the biometric system to be scalable to accommodate the increased number of users and access levels. The traditional approach requires the upgrading of hardware, software, and network infrastructure. To manage the growing number of users, this platform implements a unique usage-based optimization to move the least active user data to the archive every week. Considering all the preventive measures that have been considered in this design, the Secure Collapsible Makerspace is expected to serve the needs of the users efficiently and provide effective usage and data security.

E. Actuator Safety Modeling

Actuator safety modeling is an important aspect of the safe operation of actuators in both residential and industrial applications. Identifying potential hazards, evaluating risks, and integrating safety features to prevent accidents and protect users and equipment from harm produce safety-optimized equipment [22]. Safety optimization is an important element in the design of the Secure Collapsible Makerspace considering its nature to be used by learners with minimal or no supervision. The design team has considered the users' safety by carefully estimating the actuator selection and positioning. For high accuracy control as well as additional safety measures, limit sensors are positioned in selected locations as a feedback mechanism for panel operation. In the panel's collapsible operation, electric linear actuators are positioned between the two panels as a control mechanism. The actuator's rear end is mounted on the fixed panel, while the extension rod on the actuator's front end is mounted on the collapsible panel. Actuators are positioned to establish a triangular arrangement based on the fundamentals of Pythagoras' Theorem as shown in Figure 4 [23]. Determining the minimum stroke length is essential to increasing the efficiency of these actuators [24].

When a panel or table is said to be fully closed, the minimum retracted of the actuator is defined as:

$$L_R = \sqrt{(Y_2 - Y_1)^2 + X_1^2} \tag{1}$$

When a panel or table is said to be fully opened, the maximum extended length of the actuator is defined as:

$$L_E = \sqrt{(X_1 + Y_2)^2 + Y_1^2} \tag{2}$$

The minimum actuator stroke can be determined by the difference between (1) and (2):

$$S = L_E - L_R \tag{3}$$

Table II defines the acronyms used in (1)-(3).

Fig. 4. Stroke calculation when fully (a) closed and (b) opened.

TABLE II. ACRONYM DEFINITIONS

Acronym	Definition
L_R	Maximum retracted length of the actuator when a panel or table is fully closed
L_E	Maximum extended length of the actuator when a panel or table is fully closed
Y_1	Distance (respective of the y-axis) between the actuator's rear-end mount and the panel hinge's axis of rotation
X_1	Distance (respective of the x-axis) between the actuator's rear-end mount and the panel hinge's axis of rotation
Y_2	Distance between the panel hinge's axis of rotation and the actuator's front-end mount
S	Actuator stroke, the distance of the extended length
L_P	Total length of the panel

The design of a linear actuator refers to the mechanism used to convert rotary motion into linear motion. The triangular arrangement is generally used particularly in linear applications where high accuracy and repeatability are required. The triangular calculation provides a high degree of rigidity and stability, which helps in preventing deflection and maintaining the accuracy of the linear motion. Additionally, the triangular arrangement allows for a compact and lightweight linear actuator which is particularly important in this application where space and weight are at a premium.

III. RESULTS

A. Functional Design

Figure 5 represents an overall functional block diagram, where the operational process of the platform is demonstrated. The control module and the security access block are communicated for user authentication instructions. Upon the user authentication process, the control module will instruct the sequential expansion of the door and side panels through the extension of the electric linear actuator. Each actuator's retraction and extension speeds are controlled by the dedicated driver. The panel expansion limit is triggered by the programmed limit sensor. The fully expanded panel allows the learners to engage in product design learning activities as in Figure 7. Each collapsible table is embedded with a fingerprint sensor that identifies the authorized user and monitors the usage time of the individual learners. Once the authorized user has been identified, the fingerprint sensor connected to the user authentication module will communicate with the control module to activate the desired table operation.

Fig. 5. Platform functional block diagram.

The operation of the user authentication module consists of two parts. The first part is the two-factor authentication module with integrated memory for storing fingerprint images, user ID, and passcode. The second part is the usage time data storage managed by the local SD card embedded with Wi-Fi facilities as shown in Figure 6, which adapts edge computing architecture. The edge computing architecture enables user data to be analyzed in real-time at the edge device, as in this case the biometric-integrated user authentication module, before being transmitted to the central location [25]. This enables the system to identify and respond to security threats much faster than if all the data had to be transmitted to a central location first [26].

Edge computing provides solutions to reduce costs associated with data storage and transmission. By processing and analyzing data locally, only relevant data needs to be transmitted to a central location for storage, which can significantly reduce the amount of data that needs to be transmitted especially in suburban and rural areas with limited communication infrastructure.

Fig. 6. Hardware communication with an edge computing architecture.

B. Platform Prototype and Application

The developed Secure Collapsible Makerspace was recently placed in a local school facility (Figure 7). Considering the requirement for product design learning skills, the prototype was installed in front of the existing product design workshop. In August 2022, the platform started operating and accommodated a total of 750 learners by December 2022. Engagement with the newly developed platform has significantly increased the learners' learning capacity. Figure 8 represents the pre- and post-assessment outcomes of 750 learners.

Fig. 7. Platform prototype.

Fig. 8. Learners' pre- and post-assessments.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to assess the linear relationship between learners' engagement time in the Secure Collapsible Makerspace and assessment outcome.

There was a positive correlation between the two variables of 0.72 with a corresponding p -value less than 0.001. The learners' monitoring system was triggered and successfully recorded the biometrics log-in and log-out of individual users as well as the usage time. Some recorded raw data during the event can be seen in Figure 9.

```
DATE: 01.12.2022; LOG IN TIME: 14:56:16; Teacher ID: 003;
DATE: 01.12.2022; TABLE 1 START: 15:01:05; Learner ID: 221;
DATE: 01.12.2022; TABLE 2 START: 15:02:25; Learner ID: 256;
DATE: 01.12.2022; TABLE 2 END: 17:04:51; Learner ID: 256;
DATE: 01.12.2022; TABLE 1 END: 17:06:02; Learner ID: 221;
DATE: 01.12.2022; LOG OUT TIME: 17:10:39; Teacher ID: 003;

DATE: 02.12.2022; LOG IN TIME: 14:42:31; Teacher ID: 007;
DATE: 02.12.2022; TABLE 3 START: 14:48:11; Learner ID: 703;
DATE: 02.12.2022; TABLE 1 START: 14:48:16; Learner ID: 015;
DATE: 02.12.2022; TABLE 2 START: 14:51:32; Learner ID: 038;
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Fig. 9. Learners' platform usage record sample.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Learning Enhancement with Secure Collapsible Makerspace

Currently, there are various monitoring devices and platforms used to empower STEM learning among learners [27]. The Google Classroom application is one of the most used platforms for monitoring learners' self-learning time in the product design course, especially during the pandemic [10]. Before the pandemic, the learners' independent learning time was not included in the learning assessment [28-29]. When compared to the existing product design workshop, the developed Secure Collapsible Makerspace has more flexibility to be applied to different assignments for learners due to its security and monitoring features. The platform monitoring feature has added significant value to the learners' self-learning time to be included in the assessment. The impact of self-learning time monitoring on the product design course will be determined by how it is integrated into the overall curriculum.

Balancing self-learning time with guided instructions and collaborative activities can help to maximize the benefit of both approaches and promote more effective learning outcomes. Factors that influence the outcome of the self-learning component in the product design course are flexibility, depth of learning, skill development, and time management. The Secure Collapsible Makerspace directly supports flexibility and time management by allowing learners to work at their own pace on their schedule. This flexibility was found to be beneficial for learners who have limitations in scheduling their learning time due to other commitments, especially in the post-pandemic era [30]. The depth of learning was indirectly benefited from the platform where learners had sufficient time at their comfort to delve deeper into topics that interest them and explore different design techniques and methodologies in greater detail [31].

Skill development is another factor that benefits from self-learning time, which allows learners to practice and develop their skills and helps them become more proficient in software design, prototyping, and product testing. However, there are several drawbacks to self-learning time in the product design course, including the lack of guidance, isolation, and the lack of motivation to engage in self-learning activities [32]. During

five months of intervention, it has been significantly recognized that the self-operative, secure, embedded with user monitoring, Secure Collapsible Makerspace encourages a significant increase in self-learning time against the assessment. As a result, the developed platform can help both learners and teachers improve the learning efficiency and productivity of the product design course. As a real-world application system, the developed monitoring platform has been applied for a patent that improves the self-learning practice among learners and brings a significant increase in knowledge and skills in the product design course. Unlike other monitoring platforms on the market, this platform can be used as a mobile multi-purpose monitoring platform at schools and community learning centers.

V. CONCLUSION

The Secure Collapsible Makerspace has been developed to assist learners in hands-on activity-related learning. The platform is driven by a control module that integrates electric linear actuators, limit sensors, and a biometric security system to ensure an expandable and secure environment. The platform is further empowered with edge computing and biometric security technology to facilitate real-time analysis of the users' makerspace utilization. The design has the option to transfer the recorded data to the cloud instantly or store it locally and transfer it when a reliable connection is available. The compact Secure Collapsible Makerspace provides learners with easy, yet secure access control without time constraints. At the same time, the teachers can remotely access the data on the cloud for learners' monitoring and assessment purposes. During the five months of the school intervention study, the platform successfully recorded learners' utilization information for the teachers to evaluate learners' performance in product design against self-learning time. The study observation concluded that the learners' productivity in the product design course can be increased with freely available and secure learning space. Self-learning monitoring Secure Collapsible Makerspace revolutionizes education by offering dynamic, personalized, and accessible learning experiences compared to conventional static learning spaces.

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Prediction of SACCOS Failure in Tanzania using Machine Learning Models

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ABSTRACT

Savings and Credit Co-Operative Societies (SACCOS) are seen as viable opportunities to promote financial inclusion and overall socioeconomic development. Despite the positive outlook for socioeconomic progress, recent observations have highlighted instances of SACCOS failures. For example, the number of SACCOS decreased from 4,177 in 2018 to 3,714 in 2019, and the value of shares held by SACCOS members in Tanzania dropped from Tshs 57.06 billion to 53.63 billion in 2018. In particular, there is limited focus on predicting SACCOS failures in Tanzania using predictive models. In this study, data were collected using a questionnaire from 880 members of SACCOS, using a stratified random sampling technique. The collected data was analyzed using machine learning models, including Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), K Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). The results showed that RF was the most effective model to classify and predict failures, followed by LR and KNN, while the results of SVM were not satisfactory. The findings show that RF is the most suitable model to predict SACCOS failures in Tanzania, challenging the common use of regression models in microfinance institutions. Consequently, the RF model could be considered when formulating policies related to SACCOS performance evaluation.

Keywords-microfinance; SACCOS; machine learning; prediction; classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Savings and Credit Co-Operative Societies (SACCOS) have been providing great solution to people with economic challenges [1]. Several researchers have appreciated the importance of SACCOS on socioeconomic development at both individual and community levels around the world [2]. SACCOS serve as engines for enhancing financial and human resources which contribute much to the national development [3]. The ability of SACCOS to facilitate capital accumulation and provide loans for various social needs, such as housing,

education, and community development, underscores their importance in enhancing the well-being of their members [4-8].

Despite the several advantages of SACCOS to the economic development, there is still however a growing concern about the high decrease in the number of SACCOS and the decrease in the value of shares among members [4]. This study addresses the issue of SACCOS failures which have been caused by challenges such as improper utilization of loans acquired, lack of financial management knowledge, poor loan repayment, weak leadership, financial constraints, and

unreliable interest rates [5]. Many researches have shown financial and operational sustainability issues within SACCOS which indicates the need for comprehensive investigation and predictive models [6]. Although previous studies have explored failures in microfinance institutions, limited attention has been paid to SACCOS, and existing research focuses primarily on the current state rather than predicting failures. This study seeks to bridge this gap by employing a prediction model to anticipate SACCOS failures in Tanzania to contribute valuable information that can inform policies and strategies to prevent and address challenges within SACCOS, ensuring their continued positive impact on economic development and financial inclusion.

II. RELATED WORKS

SACCOS have been regarded as an eye towards financial inclusion in an economy where many people are facing financial challenges [7-8]. SACCOS have become triggers for mobilizing financial resources, human resources, and capital for national development [9]. SACCOS help their members accumulate capital and loans for social needs, such as building houses, buying clothes, paying school fees, hosting weddings, and other social activities [10]. They enable easy access to financial services, encourage savings, create employment opportunities, and directly support community development efforts, such as enabling community access to social services for stimulated growth [11-12]. SACCOS make finance more accessible to underprivileged members, limit financial exclusion, stimulate a thrift culture, help bring awareness to ordinary people of how to create assets, and generally improve the economic performance of developing countries [12].

SACCOS in Tanzania have a history dating back to 1930. The total of loans issued by SACCOS in Tanzania increased to 927.66 billion in 2019 from 833.89 billion, indicating increased credit to finance various economic activities. Additionally, total loans issued increased by 15.21 billion in the last quarter of 2018. The total savings of SACCOS members increased to 200.21 billion in 2019 compared to 176.48 billion in 2018. In this period, SACCOS members total deposits increased to 51.67 billion compared to 39.53 billion in December 2018. The total number of members, share values, value of deposits, savings, loans issued, and outstanding loans were found to have increased in 2019. Regardless of such socioeconomic development and contributions, some unexpected issues were observed. For example, the number of SACCOS decreased from 4,177 at the end of 2018 to 3,714 at the end of 2019. The value of shares of SACCOS members in the country decreased to 53.63 billion in 2019 compared to 57.06 billion in 2018. The above-given statistics signal SACCOS failures. In [12], SACCOS failures were attributed to various challenges such as improper utilization of loans taken, lack of knowledge in financial management, and poor repayment of loans taken by members. In Tanzania, SACCOS fail to deliver adequate socioeconomic benefits to members due to both internal and external factors, which may generally include financial constraints, weak leadership, unreliable interest rates of loans, and poor record-keeping systems. Out of 103 SACCOS in Tanzania, 61% of them fail to be sustainable operationally and 51% of them fail financially.

SACCOS failure has previously been studied in [9-10, 12, 13]. Most studies have investigated the existing situation of SACCOS and not the prediction of the failure of given SACCOS. Other studies have used prediction models but not in SACCOS. This study sheds light on the pressing issue of SACCOS failures, emphasizing the need for proactive measures to ensure their sustained socioeconomic impact. This study used machine learning models to provide a valuable tool for predicting potential failures, offering a strategic approach to address the challenges faced by SACCOS. The experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness in classifying datasets, further underscoring its potential practical applications. As SACCOS continue to be crucial to financial inclusion and community development, the insights derived contribute to a broader discourse on mitigating operational and financial risks within cooperative societies. Moving forward, policymakers, regulatory bodies, and stakeholders can take advantage of these findings to implement informed strategies to strengthen the resilience of SACCOS and sustain their positive impact on economic growth and social well-being.

III. THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

This study used a quantitative approach aligned with its objective of focusing on causal-effect relationships utilizing statistical data to optimize efficiency and resource utilization. Employing an explanatory cross-sectional survey research design, the study analyzes each targeted SACCOS as a unit of analysis across diverse regions in Tanzania. This design allows for a comprehensive examination of the failure information among the SACCOS surveyed. The research spans five key regions: Dar es Salaam, Arusha, Mbeya, Mwanza, and Dodoma, which not only host a significant concentration of SACCOS but also represent major zones in Tanzania. In particular, the high-risk nature of SACCOS in these regions is acknowledged by the Tanzania Cooperative Development Commission (TCDC). The study strategically involved SACCOS members as primary informants due to their deep knowledge of key figures, such as staff, management, and TCDC representatives, to retrieve comprehensive information on SACCOS performance. Units of analysis predominantly focus on SACCOS, given the relatively limited exploration of their performance compared to other Microfinance Institutions (MFIs). The sample size, determined using (1) [14-15], involved 880 SACCOS members in the specified regions, allowing for a nuanced examination of factors that contribute to their success or failure. This research design encompasses geographic diversity and key informant perspectives and enables the study to offer valuable information on the dynamics of SACCOS failures in Tanzania.

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pqN}{e^2(N-1) + Z^2 pq} \quad (1)$$

In (1), n is the sample size for a finite population, N is the population size, p is the population reliability or the estimated frequency for a sample of size n , which was 0.5 as used for the population of all developing countries, $p + q = 1$, e is the margin of error considered 3%, and Z is the normal reduced variable, which at the 0.05 level of significance is 1.96 giving a sample size of 880.

Concerning the predictive model for SACCOS failure in Tanzania, the focus encompasses two primary aspects: the formulation of a suitable model to predict SACCOS failure and the subsequent validation of its accuracy and efficacy. These tasks were accomplished using machine-learning models [16-19]. Throughout this process, the dependent variable was identified as SACCOS Failure (*SP*), while the independent variables were Return on Assets (*RA*), SACCOS Size (*SS*), SACCOS Members (*SM*), SACCOS Assets (*SA*), Deposits Mobilization (*DM*), Interest Rate (*IR*), and Age of SACCOS (*AS*). The resulting model is expressed by:

$$SP = \beta_1 RA + \beta_2 SS + \beta_3 SM + \beta_4 SA + \beta_5 DM + \beta_6 IR + \beta_7 AS \quad (2)$$

where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6,$ and β_7 are estimated regression coefficients that represent the change in *SP* relative to one unit in change in the respective independent variable. The values of the regression coefficients were estimated from the dataset used in the study. The resulting values of each regression coefficient were: $\beta_1 = -153.8069, \beta_2 = 153.9002, \beta_3 = 154.6836, \beta_4 = -153.8151, \beta_5 = 0.00001215, \beta_6 = 0.0009,$ and $\beta_7 = 0.0495$. The dependent variable was computed using:

$$SF = \frac{\text{SACCOS Operating Income (SOI)}}{\text{SACCOS OPERATING Expenses (SOE)}} \quad (3)$$

The descriptions of the independent variables were made as follows: *RA* is the ratio of the total SACCOS income to the average total SACCOS assets (4), where the average total SACCOS assets is the ratio of the total assets to the total members of *SS* expressed by (5):

$$RA = \frac{\text{Income}}{\text{Average Total Asset}} \quad (4)$$

$$SS = \ln(\text{Total SACCOS Income}) \quad (5)$$

$$DM = \frac{\text{Deposits}}{\text{Loans}} \quad (6)$$

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The sample size of this study comprised 880 individuals drawn from SACCOS members across diverse regions of Tanzania. To develop and validate the prediction model for SACCOS failure, the dataset was partitioned into training data (80%) and testing data (20%). The training data, serve as the foundation for instructing machine learning models, including KNN, SVM, LR, and RF. KNN operates by classifying data points based on the majority class within their proximity. SVM constructs a hyperplane to segregate classes, aiming to maximize the margin between them. LR models the probability of an event occurring, and RF employs an ensemble of decision trees for classification. Each method presents distinct advantages and disadvantages. KNN is simple and effective but can be computationally expensive. SVM is robust in high-dimensional spaces but may struggle with larger datasets. LR is interpretable and efficient but assumes linear relationships. RF excels in handling complex datasets but may overfit with noisy data. The performance of these methods was evaluated through

the training and testing phases, considering their respective strengths and limitations in predicting SACCOS failure. Table I shows the performance of each algorithm based on the sample size.

TABLE I. MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR SACCOS FAILURE PREDICTION

Index	SVM	LR	KNN	RF
Accuracy	0.6498	0.9663	0.8232	1.0000
Recall	0.0000	0.9999	0.8043	1.0000
AUC	0.7722	0.9999	0.9012	1.0000
Precision	0.0000	0.9159	0.7208	1.0000

Table I presents an evaluation of different machine learning models for predicting SACCOS failure based on training and test datasets. The SVM model showed suboptimal performance with recall and precision scores of 0%, an Area Under the Curve (AUC) score of approximately 77%, and an accuracy score of approximately 65%. These results indicate that SVM is not suitable for predicting SACCOS failure in Tanzania. In contrast, the LR model exhibited superior performance with approximately 99% recall, 91.59% precision, 100% AUC, and 99.63% accuracy. Similarly, the KNN model presented significant index scores, including approximately 80% recall, 72% precision, 90% AUC, and 82% accuracy. Finally, the RF model demonstrated exceptional performance with perfect scores in all indices, indicating that it is the most effective model for classifying SACCOS failure compared to the other models tested in this study. These findings reveal distinctive results for each algorithm, as reflected in their respective confusion matrices. For SVM, the recall and precision scores both registered 0%, underscoring its limitations in correctly identifying true positives and minimizing false positives. LR, on the other hand, exhibited remarkable performance, with high recall, precision, AUC, and accuracy scores, indicating its efficacy in capturing true positive instances while maintaining precision. KNN demonstrated significant recall and precision scores, emphasizing its ability to correctly classify positive instances with a balanced precision rate. RF presented perfect scores on all indices of the confusion matrix, showcasing its unparalleled ability to correctly identify true positives, minimize false positives and negatives, and achieve overall accuracy. The confusion matrices shown in Figures 1-4 offer insight into the performance of the models.

Fig. 1. Confusion matrix for SACCOS failure prediction using SVM.

Fig. 2. Confusion matrix for SACCOS failure prediction using KNN.

Fig. 3. Confusion matrix for SACCOS failure prediction using LR.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix for SACCOS failure prediction using RF.

A comparison was carried out using ROC curves to evaluate the four considered machine-learning models. Figure 5 illustrates that the RF model's curve ranks highest with an AUC of 1.00, followed by the LR model with an AUC of 1.00, the KNN model with an AUC of 0.90, and the SVM model at the bottom with an AUC of 0.77.

This comparative analysis indicates that RF excels as the premier model for classifying the dataset, followed by LR and KNN, while SVM exhibits comparatively inferior performance. These findings align consistently with the individual model evaluations discussed earlier. In summary, although KNN and LR demonstrate commendable performance in classifying the dataset, RF emerges as the optimal model in this study for predicting SACCOS failure in Tanzania. Furthermore, with a 100% accuracy rate, RF proves to be an exceptionally effective model in anticipating SACCOS failure in the Tanzanian

context, as shown through the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve in Figure 5. Recommendations include integrating predictive analytics into SACCOS management, fostering financial literacy programs, and implementing stringent loan utilization monitoring. Such measures can fortify SACCOS resilience, ensuring sustained socio-economic contributions and mitigating operational risks.

Fig. 5. The ROC curve for comparison of the machine learning models.

The ROC curves for the four machine-learning algorithms indicate distinct performances. The RF model demonstrated the highest performance, with an AUC of 1.00, followed by LR with an AUC of 1.00, KNN with an AUC of 0.90, and SVM with the lowest AUC of 0.77. This comparison underscores RF as the superior model in classifying the dataset, with LR and KNN following closely. The analysis of the ROC curve reaffirms the findings discussed above, highlighting the predictive efficacy of RF in anticipating SACCOS failure.

V. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the critical issue of SACCOS failure, employing a quantitative approach and an explanatory cross-sectional survey research design. The study collected and analyzed data from 880 SACCOS members in five key regions in Tanzania. Examination of four machine-learning models, SVM, LR, KNN, and RF, revealed significant disparities in predictive efficacy. The RF model emerged as the optimal choice, boasting a 100% accuracy rate, making it the most effective for anticipating SACCOS failure. Recommendations include integrating predictive analytics into SACCOS management practices, improving financial literacy initiatives, and implementing robust monitoring mechanisms for loan utilization. These measures aim to strengthen the resilience of SACCOS, ensuring sustained socioeconomic contributions and mitigating operational risks in the microfinance sector.

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Machine Learning-assisted Prediction and Optimization of Exergy Efficiency and Destruction of Cumene Plant under Uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

Machine Learning (ML)'s growing role in process industries during the digitalization era is notable. This study combines Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Aspen Plus to predict exergy efficiency, exergy destruction, and potential improvements in a cumene plant under uncertain process conditions. An optimization framework, using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA), was developed to enhance exergy efficiency amid uncertainty. Initially, a steady-state Aspen model evaluates exergy efficiency, irreversibility, and potential improvements. The proposed model is transitioned to a dynamic mode, introducing artificial uncertainties into key variables. An ANN model predicts exergy efficiency and exergy destruction under uncertainty. The PSO and GA-based optimization methods improve exergy efficiency and reduce exergy destruction. This work demonstrates the potential real-time application of intelligent methods in plant analysis.

Keywords-exergy analysis; digitalization; industry 4.0; machine learning; process uncertainties

I. INTRODUCTION

Cumene, a key chemical reagent, finds extensive applications in phenol and acetone production, forming the basis for about 98% of acetone and phenol manufacturing [1]. The world's 80% plastic demand is met by phenol and acetone-derived polymers, while about 98% of acetone and phenol production is based on cumene [2-4]. Forecasts indicate a substantial rise in global cumene demand, expected to reach USD 17.63 billion by 2025. To address this demand and enhance product quality while optimizing resource utilization, efforts are focused on exploring efficient cumene production processes. Computational methods play a crucial role in this endeavor, enabling the investigation of various aspects, including design enhancements, yield improvements, process control, and environmental impact [1]. Notable changes in design optimization have led to a 47% reduction in Total Annualized Cost (TAC) through the replacement of conventional distillation columns with reactive distillation and topological changes [5, 6]. Single dividing wall columns have

replaced traditional ones, saving up to 18.75% in TAC [5]. Process parameter optimization, utilizing Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and Genetic Algorithm (GA), has achieved higher net present values and yield improvements [5-7]. Plant-wide control structures ensure production stability, with two advanced approaches offering superior performance [8, 9]. Multi-Objective Optimization (MOO) addresses environmental, safety, and economic aspects, optimizing material losses and process safety [14, 15]. Dynamic simulations identify key factors in cumene conversion and downstream distillation column overpressure [16]. The comparative study in [17] highlights intensified processes' economic attractiveness and environmental friendliness.

Exergy analysis is emerging as a prominent approach to enhance energy efficiency in cumene production, with potential applications from other industries [18-23]. Exergy analysis was performed on a cumene production plant utilizing Aspen Plus and MATLAB in [24]. The plant was divided into preheating, reaction, and separation segments, and physical and chemical

exergy computations were conducted. The overall plant exergy efficiency achieved an impressive 84.93%.

The integration of machine learning into AI for exergy analysis has been explored in the literature. In [25], a Machine Learning (ML) model was devised to predict the exergy efficiency of a blast furnace. Subsequently, an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model was developed to forecast exergy efficiency, relying on 11 uncertain process variables. In [26], a combination of Straight Run (SR), GA, and ANN models was employed to evaluate the impact of uncertainty in process conditions and crude composition on furnace exergy efficiency. Similarly, a study involved the development and comparison of Bootstrap Aggregating (bagging) and Random Forest (RF) models for predicting VDU exergy efficiency under uncertain process parameters [24]. Another study delved into the repercussions of process condition uncertainty on the overall exergy efficiency of naphtha reforming, employing an RF model with a Bootstrap Filter (BF) [27]. The present study builds upon the foundation laid in [24], introducing ML-based prediction and optimization concepts to enhance exergy efficiency and minimize exergy destruction. The major contributions of this study are:

- Development of dynamic modeling of the cumene production process through incorporation of uncertainty in a steady state process model and calculation of variations in exergy efficiency and exergy destruction.
- Development of an ANN-based model for the estimation of the process exergy efficiency and destruction.
- Development of an optimization framework based on GA and PSO to achieve higher exergy efficiency of the process.

II. THEORETICAL FUNDAMENTALS

A. Process Description

This study considers the process that involves feed preheating, reactor reactions, and component separation in the depropanizer and benzene columns, as shown in Figure 1. In the Preheating and Reactive segment, the process involves warming propene, benzene feeds, and recycled benzene from the separation section using heat from the reactor's outlet stream (Reac-Out). Propene is heated by the heat exchanger (E-2), while benzene feeds and recycled benzene are warmed by a separate heat exchanger (E-1). After preheating, the streams are blended to reach the required reaction temperature. Then, a furnace (H-1) further raises the temperature before introducing the stream into the reactor (R-1) for alkylation and transalkylation reactions. The reactor effluent's heat is exchanged with incoming feeds in heat exchangers (E-3 and E-2) for energy efficiency. Effluent temperature is reduced to the propene column temperature via a Waste Heat Boiler (WHB). Moving to the Separation phase, the reactor effluent enters the depropanizer column for component separation based on boiling points. The upper output provides unreacted propylene and inert propane, while the lateral output supplies fuel gas. The lower stream (Sep-1 Bottoms) from the depropanizer column containing benzene, cumene, and DIBP (diisopropylbenzene), exchanges heat with other process streams using the heat exchanger (E-1) before entering the

benzene column. The unreacted benzene is the upper output in the benzene column, while cumene and DIPB comprise the lower output. DIPB-containing lower stream is treated as waste, and cumene is collected from the upper part of the cumene recovery column.

Fig. 1. Cumene process flow diagram.

B. Exergy Performance Indicators

Exergy analysis is a fundamental tool utilized in assessing the thermodynamic performance of a system. It encompasses the evaluation of system exergy efficiency and exergy destruction. Irreversibility serves as a quantification of the exergy destroyed within a processing unit, measured by the disparity between exergy inflows and outflows from the unit streams, as defined by:

$$I = \dot{E}x_{destroyed} = \sum \dot{E}x_{in} - \sum \dot{E}x_{out} \quad (1)$$

The irreversibility of a distillation column, on the other hand, is determined by (2) which considers the heat duty of the reboiler and condenser (Q_r and Q_c) as well as the respective temperatures (T_r and T_c).

$$I = \dot{E}x_{destroyed} = \sum \left(\dot{E}x_{feed} + \left(1 - \frac{T_o}{T_r}\right) Q_r \right) - \sum \left(\dot{E}x_{product} + \left(1 - \frac{T_o}{T_c}\right) Q_c \right) \quad (2)$$

The concept of exergy efficiency, on the other hand, gauges the degree of system proximity to an ideal state. In reversible conditions, exergy efficiency denotes the system's effectiveness relative to optimal performance. While various exergy efficiency formulas exist in the literature, the widely adopted and straightforward approach is the universal exergy efficiency, which represents the ratio of useful exergy output to input, as expressed in (3):

$$\varphi_{universal} = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in}} \quad (3)$$

This metric provides a concise measure of system performance and aids in assessing the effectiveness of energy utilization within the analyzed process.

C. Artificial Neural Networks

ANNs encompass a suite of algorithms that replicate human brain operations, enabling quantitative data interpretation through training/learning procedures. Comprising three layer types -input, hidden, and output- an ANN incorporates interconnected neurons to model intricate and nonlinear functions. The input layer receives external environmental information or features, while neurons within the hidden layers extract system-related data. Neurons process inputs via predetermined activation functions, employing associated weights for calculations. For each input variable, the neuron's output is determined through a nonlinear amalgamation of inputs (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) and corresponding weights (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n). Conclusively, the output neuron layer generates and showcases the network's ultimate outputs, derived from prior-layer neuron processing activities.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employed an integrated environment consisting of Aspen Plus and MATLAB to conduct an exergy analysis of a cumene producing plant. The following steps were followed:

1. The EXERGYFL property set of Aspen Plus was utilized to calculate the physical energy of the system.
2. MATLAB was integrated with Aspen Plus through their interface to determine the chemical exergy of the process.
3. The cumene production process was divided into sections treated as control volumes. The exergy entering each section was computed by considering the streams entering the control volume, while the energy leaving the section was considered as the outlet energy of the streams.
4. Irreversibility equations were utilized to calculate the values of irreversibility for each section.
5. The exergy efficiency, which represents the potential for exergetic improvement, was calculated based on the obtained exergy analysis results.
6. Data sets for ANN training and testing were generated by introducing artificial uncertainties of $\pm 10\%$ in the steady state values by integrating MATLAB and Aspen PLUS. The 80% of the data were used for training the ANN and 20% for testing.
7. Finally, an optimization framework based on GA and PSO was developed for achieving higher exergy efficiency and lower exergy destruction of the process.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents the results and discussion of the prediction of exergy destruction and exergy efficiency in the cumene production process using an ANN. The ANN model was trained and validated using a comprehensive dataset. The trained model was then utilized to predict the exergy efficiency and destruction of the process for various operating conditions. The results obtained from the ANN predictions are analyzed and compared with the actual exergy analysis data to assess the accuracy and reliability of the model. The implications and

significance of the findings are discussed, along with potential areas for process optimization and improvements based on the predicted exergy values.

In this study, the initial step involves performing a steady-state exergy analysis of a cumene production plant, achieved through an integrated framework of Aspen Plus and MATLAB. Subsequently, an uncertainty analysis of the cumene production plant is conducted within an integrated setting encompassing Aspen Plus, MATLAB, and Microsoft Excel's Aspen Simulation Workbook. The physical exergy is calculated with the use of MATLAB and Aspen Plus interface.

A. Exergy Efficiency

The overall plant exergy efficiency was calculated with (4) and its value is 84.89. In (4), E_{out} is the overall total exergy out from the system and E_{in} is the overall total exergy entering the system.

$$\eta = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in}} \quad (4)$$

For the analysis of a cumene production plant, 9 input variables which are affecting the production and the efficiency of the cumene plant are selected. In these 9 input variables, an uncertainty of $\pm 10\%$ is introduced for the analysis (Table I). These input variables include the entering flow rates of propylene and benzene, the outlet pressures of Pump-1 and Pump-2, the heater outlet temperature, the mole fractions of propylene and propane, and the outlet pressure and temperature of the Heat Exchanger-1. The data distribution of all the input variables is shown in Figures 2-10.

Fig. 2. Propylene feed flow vs number of samples.

Fig. 3. Propylene mole fraction vs number of samples.

Fig. 4. Propane mole fraction vs number of samples.

Fig. 5. Outlet pressure of Pump-1.

Fig. 6. Benzene flow rate vs number of samples.

Fig. 7. Heat Exchanger-1 outlet pressure vs number of samples.

Fig. 8. Heater-1 outlet temperature vs number of samples.

Fig. 9. Heat Exchanger-1 outlet values vs number of samples.

Fig. 10. Heat Exchanger-1 outlet pressure vs number of samples.

Table I shows the original values of the process conditions and their corresponding modified values by inserting uncertainty. From Table I we can see the effect of the uncertainty on the overall exergy efficiency of the cumene plant. For instance, in case of the heater outlet temperature at steady state and after introducing the uncertainty, there is a significant difference between the reported values. For instance, the steady state heater outlet temperature is 623.15 K and in case 1 and case 2 it is 640.79 K and 592.61 K, respectively.

TABLE I. ORIGINAL AND MODIFIED (WITH UNCERTAINTY) INPUT AND OUTPUT PROCESS VARIABLES

	Variable	Values	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Input	Propylene flowrate	0.029	0.028251	0.028686	0.029324	0.028262	0.029537
	Propylene mole fraction	0.95	0.9082	0.90649	0.909245	0.95209	0.911715
	Propane mole fraction	0.05	0.0918	0.09351	0.090755	0.04791	0.088285
	Outlet pressure of Pump-1	2451662.5	2537716	2557084	2499960	2472011	2528890
	Benzene flowrate	0.027	0.028006	0.028806	0.027125	0.027272	0.026719
	Outlet pressure of Pump-2	2533125	2548070	2494622	2519446	2420148	2451305
	Heater-1 outlet temperature	623.15	640.7851	592.6157	644.524	649.4469	640.0374
	Heat Exchanger-1 outlet temperature	363.15	347.1714	346.5177	347.5709	363.9489	348.5151
Heat Exchanger-1 outlet pressure	245166	246612.5	241439.5	243842.1	234231.6	237247.1	
Output	Overall plant exergy efficiency	84.888	84.79163	84.95358	84.78349	84.80763	84.806

To carry out the analysis of cumene production plant we developed a data set consisting of 200 samples, with changes in the selected 9 input variables. From physical and chemical exergy we found the total exergy of each piece of equipment and then with these values we found the overall plant exergy efficiency. After calculating all the respective values, MATLAB environment was used to develop the ANN model. The model has 5 hidden layers with 18, 13, 11, 13, and 18 neurons, respectively. The utilized model training method was Levenberg-Marquardt. The values of RMSE, MSE, and R^2 of the model are 0.115, 0.0133, and 0.1466, respectively. Figure 11 shows the training state of the model. The training R^2 value is 0.996. After training the ANN model, for testing we gave the input data to the ANN for predicting the output against those values. Figure 12 shows the result. Figure 13 is a regression graph of the ANN model predicted versus the targeted values of exergy efficiency. The testing R value is 0.923. Figure 14 shows the performance of the ANN model in the prediction of the targeted Aspen model values.

Fig. 11. Performance of the ANN model on the training data for the prediction of exergy efficiency.

To boost the exergy efficiency of the cumene production process, PSO and GA algorithms are employed, utilizing a trained ANN model for optimization under uncertainty. The exergy efficiency comparison is detailed in Table II, encompassing the SA, GA, and PSO models. Figures 14 and 15 illustrate the exergy efficiency disparities among the models. The SA model, an unoptimized Aspen first-principle model under uncertainty, exhibits lower exergy efficiency compared to GA and PSO models. For example, in data sample 1, the SA model achieves 84.89% exergy efficiency, while the GA and PSO optimizations result in 89.46% and 89.54%, respectively. Similar trends are observed in data sample 2, with the SA model at 85.47% and the GA and PSO optimizations reaching 86.09% and 88.20%, respectively.

Fig. 12. Performance of the ANN model on the testing data for the prediction of exergy efficiency.

Fig. 13. Performance of the ANN model vs the number of samples.

TABLE II. EXERGY EFFICIENCY COMPARISON

Data sample	Exergy efficiency (%)		
	SA	GA-optimized	PSO-optimized
1	84.89	89.46	89.54
2	85.47	86.09	88.20
3	84.83	89.49	89.66
4	84.68	89.72	89.81
5	85.09	86.22	86.26
6	85.39	89.24	89.54
7	84.80	88.95	89.54
8	84.93	89.29	89.57
9	85.12	89.47	89.62
10	84.80	88.96	88.97

B. Exergy Destruction

Again, we created a dataset with 200 samples with changes in the selected 9 input variables. From physical and chemical exergy, we found the total exergy of each piece of equipment and with these values we find out the overall plant exergy destruction.

Fig. 14. Comparison of SA and GA exergy efficiency.

Fig. 15. Comparison of SA and PSO exergy efficiency.

Fig. 16. Performance of the ANN model on the training data for the prediction of exergy destruction.

After calculating all the respective values, the ANN model was constructed in MATLAB. The model has 5 hidden layers with 18, 18, 12, 18, and 18 neurons. The Levenberg-Marquardt

training method was utilized. The values of RMSE, MSE, and R^2 of the model are $1.4790e+03$, $2.1875e+06$, and 0.8930, respectively. Figure 17 shows the training state of the model. The training R value is 0.998.

Fig. 17. Performance of the ANN model on the testing data for the prediction of exergy destruction.

Figure 18 shows a regression graph of the ANN model predicted exergy destruction values versus the targeted values. The testing R-value is 0.932. Figure 18 shows how efficient the ANN model is for the prediction of the targeted values.

Fig. 18. Performance of the ANN model on the testing data for the prediction of exergy destruction.

To optimize the process of cumene production exergy destruction, PSO and GA algorithms were used with the trained ANN model for surrogate optimization under uncertainty. The comparative exergy destruction analysis is shown in Table III. Figures 19 and 20 show the exergy destruction differences between the SA, GA, and PSO models. It can be seen that the SA model, representing the initial unoptimized Aspen first-principle modeling under uncertainty, yields higher exergy destruction values than the GA and PSO models.

TABLE III. EXERGY DESTRUCTION COMPARISON

Data sample	Exergy destruction (%)		
	SA	GA-optimized	PSO-optimized
1	104236.21	94039.73	93917.13
2	100564.41	89896.23	89832.06
3	97807.401	77742.91	77374.90
4	103897.21	78950.98	78461.67
5	99689.17	92298.68	92159.99
6	94773.92	88431.85	88415.37
7	105077.15	81670.35	81332.63
8	104235.50	94178.04	93917.13
9	100564.37	90241.66	89832.06
10	105077.29	82050.40	81332.63

Fig. 19. Comparison of SA and GA exergy destruction.

Fig. 20. Comparison of SA and PSO exergy destruction.

V. DISCUSSION

The current study assessed overall plant exergy efficiency in cumene production, achieving a value of 84.89%. With 9 key input variables under $\pm 10\%$ uncertainty, visualized in Figures 2-10. The data distribution highlighted variable impact. A dataset of 200 samples was constructed. The 5-layer ANN model with Levenberg-Marquardt training in MATLAB, showed robust performance (RMSE: 0.115, MSE: 0.0133, R^2 : 0.1466). PSO and GA optimizations enhanced exergy efficiency, surpassing the unoptimized Aspen model, as evidenced in Table II and Figures 14-15 across various data samples.

For the cumene production plant's uncertainty analysis, the MATLAB-built ANN efficiently predicted the exergy destruction. The training results, illustrated in Figure 16, showed a high correlation ($R = 0.998$), with the testing results

displaying the effectiveness of the model (Figure 17, R-value: 0.932). PSO and GA optimizations, outlined in Table III and Figures 19-20, consistently outperformed the unoptimized Aspen model (SA), achieving reduced exergy destruction values across different data samples.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, steady-state exergy analysis of a cumene production plant was performed using Aspen Plus and MATLAB. Nine input variables influencing production and exergy destruction were selected for uncertainty analysis. An optimization framework with Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) was developed to enhance exergy efficiency under $\pm 10\%$ uncertainty. The analysis involved 200 data samples with variations in the 9 input variables. An ANN model with 5 hidden layers was created using Levenberg-Marquardt training. The model showed RMSE and MSE values of 0.115 and 0.0133, respectively, with a correlation coefficient of 0.92 for predicting exergy efficiency and 0.93 for exergy destruction. Both the GA and PSO-based frameworks outperformed the non-optimized model by increasing exergy efficiency and decreasing exergy destruction.

Utilizing the Artificial Neural Network (ANN), the research underscores the transformative potential of digital tools for real-time prediction of exergy efficiency and destruction, redefining process optimization and control. The current study introduces a sustainable optimization framework, employing GA and PSO for enhanced energy efficiency in manufacturing processes.

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Computational and Experimental Investigation of Thermal Generation in CNC Milling Machine Spindle Bearing with the Oil-Air Lubrication Method

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the thermal generation dynamics in the spindle unit of a CNC milling machine. The main objective is to analyze the heat transfer from the bearings to the housing during operation, using simulations and experiments. An air-oil-cooled lubrication system is employed, which enables the airflow to dissipate some of the heat produced. Before conducting the experiment, heat generation and transfer are accurately predicted. The air-oil mixture, formed by pressurized air atomizing oil droplets, is effective in cooling high-temperature regions. A spindle ER16-80SK 24k is integrated with a CNC machine for real-time data acquisition, including parameters such as spindle speed and temperature. The results show significant temperature rises in all bearings, which reach a steady state after an hour of operation. There are noticeable differences in range, from 6.1% to 43.4%, between the experimental and simulated maximum temperatures, indicating possible real factors not considered in the simulation. The environmental impacts of oil particle emission are also discussed, which require proper ventilation management during operations. This research provides valuable insight into the thermal dynamics of CNC milling machine spindles and establishes a solid basis for further research and development in this important field of machining technology.

Keywords-CNC machining; spindle unit; thermal generation; temperature monitoring; air-oil mixture lubrication

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern manufacturing requires high-speed machining, which allows for the creation of complex and advanced products [1]. The elevated rate of spindle rotation also results in increased thermal generation, which can impact rigidity and lead to warping problems. As a result, various cooling and lubrication techniques have been suggested, such as the application of air-oil cooling, which can enhance the effectiveness of both lubrication and cooling. The spindle unit's stiffness is an important factor that influences the quality of machining in machine tools [2, 3]. However, when machining at high speeds, heat is produced, lowering the

stiffness or increases the deformation of the spindle [4-7]. Hence, a variety of methods for lubrication and cooling have been suggested to reduce thermal production at bearings, such as the use of grease, oil splatter, oil fog, and a combination of air and oil [8]. Research has indicated that the pattern of temperature change over the course of operation was comparable between empirical and computational simulation studies when all the bearings of the CNC spindle unit were lubricated using grease [9]. The authors used ANSYS software to model the spindle unit and applied boundary conditions based on experimental data. They found that the maximum temperature rise occurred at the front bearing near the tool tip due to high contact pressure and friction. They also observed

that the temperature distribution was uneven along the spindle axis due to heat conduction and convection. A more efficient method of lubrication and cooling that saves lubricant and is favored in modern machining industry is oil-air mixture lubrication [10]. Oil-air mixture lubrication consists of injecting small droplets of oil mixed with air into the bearing gap. The oil droplets provide lubrication while the air provides cooling. Oil-air mixture lubrication has several advantages over grease lubrication, such as lower friction coefficient, higher heat dissipation capacity, better lubrication performance at high speeds, and longer service life [11, 12]. Several studies have investigated the effect of oil-air mixture lubrication on thermal generation in spindle bearing units using numerical simulations. Authors in [13] modeled the heat transfer process and examined the thermal coupling using finite element analysis. They considered different parameters such as oil-air ratio, injection pressure, injection angle, and spindle speed.

Although the existing literature has provided some insights into the lubrication and cooling methods for spindle bearing units, there are still some gaps and limitations that need to be addressed. Some studies have conducted experimental tests to validate the numerical results and to compare the performance of different lubrication methods under realistic conditions. For instance, authors in [14] conducted a study on the effectiveness of high-speed spindles using oil/air lubrication. Their research primarily delved into the impact of varied lubrication parameters and preloads on factors such as temperature elevation, thermal deformation, and static stiffness. Employing the Taguchi methodology, they identified the most favorable lubrication parameters that effectively minimize temperature escalation, offering valuable insights for crafting high-speed spindles endowed with adequate static stiffness. Similarly, authors in [15] scrutinized film formation under both oil-air and oil-jet lubrication systems. They found that oil-air lubrication has a better oil supply efficiency and slower decrease in film thickness in starved regime, because of the role of the micron-order oil droplets that enhance oil supply efficiency. Experimental research evaluating the effects of various lubrication and cooling methods pointed out the advantages and disadvantages of each method. In particular, the factors affecting the quality of lubrication are also clearly indicated in [16]. It was also recommended that additives can be added to the lubricating oil to improve lubrication efficiency, which can help to lower friction and component wear within the machine [17, 18].

Spindle bearings play a pivotal role in machine tools, exerting a substantial influence on the overall efficiency and precision of the machining operation. Their performance is paramount to achieving optimal productivity and impeccable quality in the process. However, spindle-bearings also generate heat due to friction and contact pressure. This generated heat has the potential to induce thermal deformations and diminish the stiffness of the spindle unit. Consequently, this could impede its load-bearing capabilities, accuracy, and overall stability. Thus, it becomes imperative to implement meticulous lubrication practices to guarantee the seamless functioning and prolonged lifespan of these bearings. Most numerical simulations have assumed ideal conditions and neglected some factors such as bearing clearance, preload, lubricant viscosity,

and environmental temperature. Moreover, there is a lack of experimental studies that validate the numerical results and to compare the performance of different lubrication methods under realistic conditions. Therefore, future research should conduct more comprehensive and realistic numerical simulations and experimental tests to evaluate the lubrication and cooling methods for spindle bearings. Furthermore, future research should also explore other factors that may affect thermal generation in spindle bearing units, such as spindle geometry, material properties, tool wear, cutting parameters, and machining strategies.

This study focuses on the thermal generation in CNC spindle-bearing units under oil-air mixture lubrication by conducting experimental tests and numerical simulations. A custom-made lubrication system was designed and built for this purpose. The system integrated mechanical, control, measurement, and monitoring components to simulate the spindle unit's operation under different lubrication modes and parameters. The system collected data for analysis after each test run. The design of the system was based on the understanding of the heat generation and transfer mechanism in the spindle unit.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Heat is generated by the spindle unit and transferred to the housing via the bearings. The airflow from the air-oil-cooled lubrication system can remove some of this heat. Before measuring the temperature of the spindle unit experimentally, it is important to predict the heat generation from the spindle and its transfer through the bearings. The air-oil mixture is produced by pumping oil from the tank to the mixer, where it is broken down by compressed air pressure, creating a powerful oil force that can reach high-temperature areas. A spindle ER16-80SK 24k, with a power capacity of 1.5 kW, was integrated with a CNC machine for the experiment, as shown in Figure 1. This spindle has 7002-type bearings and is driven by a three-phase asynchronous motor controlled by an inverter. The system monitors key parameters such as spindle speed, current, voltage, torque, and sends alarm signals when needed. Temperature sensors were attached to the bearings, allowing real-time temperature data collection, which is stored in a computer for further analysis.

Fig. 1. Cross-section of the investigated spindle unit.

The ball rotates at a velocity of ωb , which is determined by the rotational speed (V) and the rotation diameter (D) [19]. The bearing generates heat mainly due to the load torque and the ball torque. The load torque is the torque exerted by the external load on the bearing, which creates friction between the balls and the races. The ball torque is the torque needed to rotate the balls around their own axes, creating friction. Both torques are influenced by the load, speed, cage design, and lubrication conditions of the bearing. Both torques increase with increasing speed and decrease with increasing lubrication efficiency. Hence, it is essential to optimize the lubrication conditions to minimize heat generation and enhance spindle performance. The experimental setup for measuring the temperature and the consumption current of the spindle-bearing unit is illustrated in Figure 2. The temperature sensors are fixed to the outer rings of the spindle unit to observe the lubrication condition and the heat production of the bearings. The consumption current is measured by an inverter, which sends the data to the controller. These data indicate the power losses and provide information about the overall efficiency of the spindle unit. Table I presents the experimental parameters for the air-oil mixture lubrication method, such as the oil-air ratio, the injection pressure, the injection angle, and the spindle speed. These parameters influence the lubrication and cooling performance of the air-oil mixture, as well as the thermal behavior of the spindle-bearing unit. The Table also displays the ambient temperature and air pressure of the environment, which are kept constant at 25 °C and 1 bar, respectively. The experiment will show how different lubrication methods and parameters affect the temperature rise and the consumption current of the spindle-bearing unit during high-speed machining. This will help the designer to compare and evaluate the performance of different lubrication methods and parameters, and to choose the best one for minimizing thermal generation and improving machining quality and efficiency.

Fig. 2. Experimental system for spindle unit integration.

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS WITH THE METHOD OF LUBRICATION USING THE AIR-OIL MIXTURE

Specification	Value
Air pressure	7.5 bar
Air flow rate	1200 l/hr
Oil flow rate	180 mm ³ /hr
Oil type	Tona 68
Spindle speed	7000 rpm
Applied load on spindle	16 N
Observation time	3600 s

The machine tool's spindle unit undergoes continuous lubrication and cooling through the air-oil method during operation. Maintaining optimal performance is contingent upon vigilant monitoring and upkeep of the lubrication status. This is done by monitoring parameters such as bearing temperature, oil level, air pressure, and spindle consumption current. To ensure proper oil flow and to optimize the lubrication and cooling process, the air pressure is kept at 7.5 bar. The other working parameters of the system are also presented in Table I. The spindle consumption current is carefully measured by an inverter, which sends the data to the controller. This preventive measure avoids system errors in case the required amount of lubricating oil is not supplied. If the bearing temperature and the consumption current increase to a predetermined limit, while all other conditions are satisfied, the system will shut down and trigger an alarm. The controller only allows the operation of the oil pump and the air valve when all criteria are met. For the numerical simulation of the lubrication and cooling process based on NX's software® using the air-oil mixture, Tona 68 lubricating oil with a kinematic viscosity of 68 mm²/s at 40 °C was used. The spindle material was carbon steel C45. Using software, a heat transfer simulation model was created, consisting of 355,237 elements. The element sizes were automatically set as 3 mm, 6 mm, and 12 mm, depending on their location on the model, as shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. The element mesh size of the simulation model.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The assessment of the temperature generated at the bearings of the CNC milling machine spindle unit involved a comparative analysis between numerical simulations and experimental findings, conducted under identical operational parameters. The CNC milling machine spindle was configured to rotate at a constant speed of 7000 rpm. Subsequently, numerical simulations were performed, followed by the collection of experimental temperature data at the spindle bearings over a working duration of 1 hr. To facilitate this, temperature sensors were strategically positioned at the bearing locations to acquire the requisite experimental data. Figure 4 shows the heat generation in the bearings 1, 3, and 4 during operation. The Figure reveals that the temperature of all bearings increases rapidly from the start of operation until around 2250 s. Then, the temperature rise slows down and the temperature reaches a relatively stable level. After 1 hr of operation, the temperature changes slightly and stabilizes. However, the stable temperature value among bearings differs. The highest temperature, 45.6 °C, is observed at bearing 4, while the lowest temperature, which is 42 °C, is observed at bearing 3. This is the lowest temperature among the bearings of

the main spindle unit. This can be explained by the fact that bearing 3 is closer to the nozzle that sprays the air-oil mixture than the other bearings. The temperature of bearing 1 is 44 °C, which is lower than bearing 4 and higher than bearing 3. This can be attributed to the fact that the nozzle that lubricates and cools with the air-oil mixture is closer to bearing 1 than to bearing 4.

Fig. 4. Simulation data-based distribution of bearing temperature during 1 hr of spindle operation at 7000 rpm.

Fig. 5. Experimental data-based measurement of bearing temperature during 1 hr of spindle operation at 7000 rpm.

The experimental results concerning the heat generated at the rolling bearings of the spindle unit, depicted in Figure 5, demonstrate a correlation in the temporal temperature variations with those observed in the simulation. Initially, there is a prominent inclination for temperature to rise until approximately 2000 s of operation. Subsequently, this escalating trend begins to subside and stabilizes after roughly 1 hr of operation. This characteristic aligns with the simulation results. However, notable disparities exist in the maximum temperature values at different rolling bearing positions compared to the simulated values. Specifically, at bearing 1, the highest temperature recorded was 46.69 °C (corresponding to an increase of 6.1% compared to the simulated value). Similarly, at bearing 3, the maximum temperature reached 60.25 °C (equivalent to a 43.4% increase when compared to the simulation results). Furthermore, at bearing 4, the peak

temperature was 61.38 °C (representing a 34.6% increase compared to the simulation results). These discrepancies suggest that the parameters employed in the simulation may not comprehensively encapsulate real-world factors, resulting in significant deviations. One plausible explanation may be an assumed higher working environment temperature in the simulation. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze the impact of other factors such as the environment and material parameters that closely match reality. This not only provides a foundation for augmenting, constructing, and refining the simulation parameters but also ensures that computational results under different lubrication modes closely emulate the actual operation of the spindle unit.

Fig. 6. Temperature comparison between experiment and simulation at bearings.

The illustrative data in Figure 6 show the similarity of the temperature increase trend in the initial working phase as well as the temperature difference between the simulation calculation and the results measured from the experiment. Additionally, the data reveal that the temperature difference is more significant at bearings 3 and 4 than at bearing 1, indicating that these bearings are more affected by the position of the gas-oil mixture nozzle and the working time of the spindle-bearing unit.

The drawbacks of other lubrication methods have been overcome using an air-oil mixture for lubrication. The bearing is supplied directly with sufficient high-pressure lubricating oil, which permeates and deeply penetrates the friction areas. To safeguard against lubricant degradation over extended periods of operation, a continuous oil supply is diligently maintained. Notably, the primary thermal zone of the rolling bearing receives a direct infusion of lubricating oil, facilitated by compressed air pressure, thereby delivering immediate cooling to the bearing balls. This approach exhibits superior lubrication efficacy compared to methods employing indirect water cooling. The application of compressed air pressure effectively fragments oil particles into minute sizes, facilitating their ingress into frictional areas and thereby heightening lubrication efficiency. Furthermore, this pressure augmentation bolsters the efficiency of the heat exchange process with the surrounding environment. The air-oil mixture lubrication method emerges as a fitting choice, particularly for high-speed processing

scenarios on CNC machines. Nonetheless, it is imperative to acknowledge its potential impact on the environment, given the discharge of oil particles post-lubrication. Thus, prudent consideration of ventilation system operation during processing is imperative.

Although there is a temperature discrepancy at the bearings of the CNC spindle between the simulation and experimental results, the simulation outcomes provide a general view of the temperature increase trend at the bearings during working stages. This can assist operators in designing appropriate lubrication regimes, ensuring system stability and the quality of the spindle unit's operation. Furthermore, experimental results are significant in evaluating the accuracy of the simulation, thereby helping designers adjust some simulation parameters or reconstruct the boundary conditions to closely match real-world working requirements. This task is still being researched and developed by our team, with the aim of constructing more suitable and realistic simulations. In addition, lubrication and cooling modes using an air-oil mixture are also being studied and experimental setups are being designed and constructed. These results will contribute to enriching lubrication and cooling modes in the field of mechanical engineering.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive investigation of the thermal generation dynamics in the spindle unit of a CNC milling machine using the oil-air lubrication method. The heat transfer from the bearings to the housing during operation is studied through a combination of computational simulations and practical experiments, providing valuable insights into the complex processes.

The results highlight the remarkable effectiveness of the air-oil mixture in absorbing and dissipating the generated heat, especially in high-temperature areas. A spindle ER16-80SK 24k is integrated with a CNC machine for experimental purposes, providing real-time data for analysis. The temperature trends in the bearings show a significant initial increase, followed by a steady state after one hour of operation. There are noticeable differences between the experimental and the simulated maximum temperatures, indicating that the simulations do not capture all the real factors. For example, the experimental temperature at bearing position 1 is 46.69 °C, which is 6.1% higher than the simulated value. Similarly, the maximum temperature at bearing position 3 is 60.25 °C, which is 43.4% higher than the simulation. The highest temperature at bearing position 4, 61.38 °C, is 34.6% higher than the simulation value. These results suggest the need for more realistic simulations in future studies. However, the study confirms the potential of the oil-air lubrication method in optimizing the spindle unit performance. The study offers practical insights for improving machining efficiency and quality, especially in high-speed machining scenarios. However, it is also important to consider the environmental impacts of oil particle emission, which require proper ventilation management during operations. This research significantly advances the understanding of thermal dynamics in CNC milling machine spindles, providing a solid foundation

for further research and development in this critical domain of machining technology.

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The Effect of Kevlar Fibers on the Mechanical Properties of Lightweight Perlite Concrete

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced concrete contains a fibrous material that increases its structural cohesion. The use of separate short fibers distributed in a random direction improves the strength of Lightweight Concrete (LWC) without exceeding its upper-density limit, improving its high fragility and mechanical properties compared to Natural-Weight Concrete (NWC). This study investigated the effect of adding Kevlar 49 fibers with three percentages of cement weight, 0.5, 1, and 1.5%, on the workability, dry density, and tensile and compressive strength of LWC. The use of Kevlar fibers in different proportions improves mechanical properties, significantly increases durability, and reduces the workability of LWC. The increase in compressive strength when adding 0.5% fibers was 19 and 15% and when adding 1% was 10 and 6%, after 7 and 28 days, respectively. At 1.5%, after 7 and 28 days, there was a decrease in compressive strength due to fiber agglomeration. Additionally, increasing the fiber dose from the optimal value caused a sharp decrease in workability by 37-40%.

Keywords-lightweight concrete; expanded perlite aggregate; silica fume; kevlar fibers

I. INTRODUCTION

There are many types of light marble since the greater their economic benefits, the greater the interest in its application in thermal insulation or in reducing dead loads, especially when used in tall buildings. The density of lightweight marble perlite aggregate used in structural concrete industries is 160-200 kg/m³ [1-2]. One of its advantages is that, according to BS EN 206-1, it contains an oven-dried density between 800 and 2000 kg/m³, where the manufacturing method is to completely or partially replace dense natural particles with lightweight sets [3-4]. According to BS EN 13055, LWC has a particle density of not more than 2.0 mg/m³ and a dry bulk density of not more than 1200 kg/m³. The distinction between these two density descriptions is that, according to BS EN 1097-33 and 1097-64, particle density refers to the mass of the separated aggregate particles per unit volume, and the bulk density is the mass of the dry fractions contained in a specified and specific volume. The aggregate that contains the least internal voids gives the lowest possible concrete density [5-6].

High-absorption materials typically result in compressive strength losses, which are typically proportionate to the replacement ratio. Low-absorption materials exhibit little fluctuations as well, and in some cases even demonstrate gains in strength and resistance. Concretes with a density of almost 2000 kg/m³ do not exhibit fluctuations in this characteristic.

Materials such as recycled glass exhibit little variation as the substitution ratio increases [7-8]. LWC is more affordable than traditional concrete due to its reduced weight, lower shipping cost, energy savings, and lower maintenance cost. This material is not commonly used in the structural industry due to its inferior mechanical qualities compared to standard concrete. Thus, Lightweight Fiber-Reinforced Concrete (LFRC) has been used in several engineering applications because it greatly enhances concrete performance by offering greater ductility than LWC, with polypropylene and steel fibers used in varied aspect ratios. Adding fibers to LWC can increase its flexural strength, tensile strength, and fracture toughness [9-11]. Fiber-Reinforced Composites (FRC) have received the most attention and have been used extensively due to their exceptional performance, high durability, affordable manufacturing cost, and superior mechanical properties, such as light weight and significant stiffness. The most important factors affecting the performance and strength of FRCs are the volume fraction, orientation, and materials of the fibers [12-14]. When a virtual crack erodes at the interface, strong and flexible kevlar fibers can extend along the grain structure to efficiently bond the local fracture, both superficial and subsurface. Using kevlar fibers in the interface can transform the bonding link by structural strengthening using carbon fibers (epoxy composite or epoxy gap repair) to a composite adhesive joint. This can be verified by examining two different surface repair tapes, epoxy

alone and containing 6 mm short kevlar fibers in gray granite samples under 3-point peak bending loads and fracture energy [15]. As LWC is considered to have low strength, the use of fibers can improve its weak strength properties while maintaining its low density. In [16], reinforced concrete with steel fibers was significantly improved using 22% polypropylene fibers, showing that concrete made of coconut fiber reinforced with sisal fiber exhibited significantly improved compressive and tensile strength after 28 days, while fiber addition of 3.0% produced a maximum increase of 14% in tensile strength. According to [17], all minimum standards were met for concrete containing 1, 2, 3, and 4% sisal fibers by cement weight [18].

This study aims to reduce the dead loads in the structural parts, which can reduce the basic cost and the vertical or lateral pressure of the casting molds, and allow investigation of the expansion effect. Perlite aggregate is considered to have compressive strength and density similar to LWC. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the effect of chemical and mineral additives to obtain the best compression resistance with the lowest density and suitable workability, in addition to determining the result of adding kevlar fibers to the performance properties of LWC and their optimal dosage.

II. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

A. Materials

Ordinary Portland cement (CEM I, 42.5R) was used conforming to [18]. Clean water was used in the mix and curing, conforming to [19]. Expanded Perlite Aggregate (EPA) was used as a fine aggregate, conforming to [20].

1) Silica Fume (SF)

SF is a very fine, sphere-shaped dust that is used as an additive to enhance concrete performance. Gray-colored SF was used. Tables I and II show its physical and chemical properties, which conform to [21].

TABLE I. CHEMICAL REQUIREMENTS OF (SF) [22]

Oxide composition	Test results %	ASTM C1240
Silicon oxide (SiO ₂)	92.84	Min(85)%
Moisture content %	0.33	Max(3)%
Loss of Ignition	1.59	Max(6)%

TABLE II. PHYSICAL REQUIREMENTS OF (SF) [22]

Physical characteristics	Test result	ASTM C1240
Flow test %	117.5	115
Accelerated pozzolanic strength activities index with the OPC at 7 days, min % of control (MPa)	107.5	Min (105)

2) Superplasticizer

BETONAC R 350 was used as a superplasticizer. It is a light brown liquid, has a density of 1.06±0.02 g/ml. Table III shows its properties [23].

3) Kevlar49 Fibers

Kevlar49 fibers have high modulus and are used in cable and rope products. Para-aramid is a strong, heat-resistant artificial fiber, associated with other aramids such as Nomex and Technora, and has a tensile strength of about 3900 GPa and

a density of 1.44 kg/m³. Table IV shows the kevlar 49 fiber properties used in this study. The percentages used were 0.5, 1, and 1.5% by concrete volume.

TABLE III. PHYSICAL REQUIREMENTS OF SUPERPLASTICIZER [24]

Property	Measurement
Appearance	Transparent or light brown liquid
Calcium chloride	Nil
Density (gm/ml)	1.10 ± 0.02
Viscosity	450 c Ps at 20 °C
Setting time	Initial and final setting time depends on temperature
Dosage	150 -1000 ml / 100 kg of cement

TABLE IV. PROPERTIES OF KEVLAR 49 FIBERS

Description*	Specification
Color	Yellow
Tensile strength (GPa)	3.9
Density (g/cm ³)	1.44
Diameter (µm)	12
Avg. length (mm)	6
Aspect ratio (L/D)	500

*Given by the manufacturer

B. LWC Design and Mixing Procedure

A group of experimental mixtures was prepared based on previous studies and research to obtain a structural LWC with the desired and suitable properties. In these mixtures, the amount of cement and water, the quality, the mineral additives, SF, and the amount of superplasticizer were changed to obtain a design strength ranging from 3.7 to 17 MPa after 7 and 28 days. Table V summarizes the design of the LWC mixtures containing 0.5, 1, and 1.5% Kevlar 49 fibers by volume of concrete, 800 ml superplasticizer for each 100 kg of cement, and 10% SF by weight of cement [22].

TABLE I. LWC MIXTURE

Mix	Ratio by volume	Cement content (kg/m ³)	EPA content (kg/m ³)	W/C	Superplasticizer (ml/100 kg)	SF (%)	Kevlar fiber (%)
MC1	1:4	247.5	113.8	0.3	800	10	0
MC2	1:4	247.5	113.8	0.3	800	10	0.5
MC3	1:4	247.5	113.8	0.3	800	10	1
MC4	1:4	247.5	113.8	0.3	800	10	1.5

C. Sample Test Methods

1) Fresh Concrete Test (Flow Testing)

The flow was tested using (1). The test stopped and a flow value was calculated after 25 strokes [24]:

$$D(\text{Flow}) = [(D - 100)/100] * 100 \quad (1)$$

where D represents the spread rate on the base diameter of the concrete.

2) Hardened Concrete Test

The oven-dried unit weight was calculated for the structural LWC using [25]:

$$Om(\text{FloDensity}) = (D * 997)/(F - G) \quad (2)$$

where O_m is the measured oven-dried density in kg/m^3 , D is the mass of the oven-dried cylinder in kg, F is the mass of the saturated surface-dry cylinder in kg, and G is the apparent mass of the suspended-immersed cylinder in kg.

a) Compressive Strength

This study used [26] to determine the compressive strength of LWC samples, using a compression device in the Construction Materials Laboratory at the University of Baghdad. The total number of cylinders used was 45 for each mixture with dimensions of 100x200 mm and a density of 800 kg/m^3 . This test was performed for concrete cylinders of 7 and 28 days of age. The compressive strength was determined using the mean of three samples for each age. Each cylinder's compressive strength was estimated by:

$$F = P/A \tag{3}$$

where F is the compressive strength in MPa, A is the loaded surface area in mm^2 , and P is the total maximum load in N.

b) Splitting Tensile Strength

Cylinder specimens with dimensions of 100x200 mm were used to determine the splitting tensile strength [10]. This test was carried out in the Construction Materials Laboratory at the University of Baghdad. The total number of cylindrical samples was 24, and the cylinders were tested after 7 and 28 days, while the mean of two cylinders was calculated by [19]:

$$T = (2 * P)/(\pi * l * d) \tag{4}$$

where T is the splitting tensile strength in MPa, l is the length of a sample in mm, P is the maximum applied load in N, and D represents the diameter in mm.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Fresh Properties

1) Flow Test

A flow test was carried out to evaluate the workability of LWC mixes according to [25]. Table VI shows the results of the flow test, indicating that increasing the kevlar fiber ratio reduces the workability of the mix, requiring the addition of a superplasticizer to keep the acceptable flow range 110 ± 5 at the same w/c ratio of 0.30. LWC containing 1 and 1.5% kevlar fibers required more superplasticizer than those containing 0 and 0.5% to achieve the specification flow. Kevlar fibers tend to consume the water in the mix, requiring increased amount of water to keep the flow within the specified range [20].

TABLE II. LWC FLOW PROPERTIES OF LWC

LWC mix	KF %	Flow (%)
MC1	0	117.75
MC2	0.5	111
MC3	1	110.7
MC4	1.5	108.25

B. Hardened Properties

1) Dry Density

Table III and Figure 1 show the oven-dried density of LWC according to [26]. The oven-dried density of MC1 indicates

that it is LWC. The density increases with kevlar fiber content because fibers tend to fill the gaps and the cellular structure from the expanded perlite addition, causing an increase in the density of LWC [27].

TABLE III. LWC DENSITY

LWC mix	KF %	Density (kg/m^3)
MC1	0	1266
MC2	0.5	1390
MC3	1	1454
MC4	1.5	1477

Fig. 1. Dry density of LWC.

2) Compressive Strength

Figure 2 and Table IV show the average values of the three cylinders recorded at 7 and 28 days of curing. For all samples, the compressive strength increased with curing age. When kevlar fibers were added, the compressive strength increased for MC2 and MC3, as the fibers work as a reinforcement for LWC, coinciding with the findings of [28-29]. For the MC4 samples, the compressive strength decreased below the value of MC1, demonstrating that excessive addition of fibers (more than 1.5%) reduces the mechanical properties of LWC, which could be attributed to slippage of the interlayers in the microstructure of LWC and Kevlar fibers.

Fig. 2. Compressive strength of LWC cured for 7 and 28 days.

TABLE IV. COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF LWC

LWC Mix	KF %	Compressive strength		Change (%)	
		7 days (MPa)	28 days (MPa)	28 days	7 days
MC1	0	10.45	14.11	-	-
MC2	0.5	12.53	16.32	15.6	19.9
MC3	1	13.86	17.41	23.4	32.6
MC4	1.5	8.7	10.33	-26.8	-16.7

3) Splitting Strength

Table V and Figure 3 show the splitting strength results of LWC cured for 7 and 28 days with and without the addition of kevlar fibers. For all samples, the splitting strength increased with curing age. The addition of kevlar fibers (MC2, MC3, and MC4) provided a substantial increase in splitting-tensile strength. The results were approximately 30% higher with the addition of 1% kevlar fibers at 28 days of curing. MC3 had the best performance, which could be possibly an indication of the good bonding between the fibers and the concrete matrix and the higher bond developed at the interface of the fiber and the concrete matrix [30].

TABLE V. SPLITTING STRENGTH OF LWC

LWC Mix	KF %	Splitting strength		Change (%)	
		7 days (MPa)	28 days (Mpa)	28 days	7 days
MC1	0	1.57	1.91	-	-
MC2	0.5	1.65	2.16	13	5.1
MC3	1	1.7	2.5	30.9	8.2
MC4	1.5	1.43	1.52	-20.4	-9

Fig. 3. Splitting strength of LWC cured for 7 and 28 days.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the best mixing ratio of LWC using lightweight Expanded Perlite Aggregate (EPA) reinforced with kevlar fibers due to its charming mechanical properties, including low density and high strength, compared to other conventional homogeneous materials. The following conclusions were drawn from this study:

- As the lightweight aggregate percentage increases, the dry density of concrete decreases in all mixture designs. After adding kevlar fibers, a slight increase in dry density was observed because.
- The workability of fresh concrete gradually decreased after adding kevlar fibers, due to the fiber agglomeration and poor distribution, as well as the high water absorption of the fiber, which requires additional mixing water.
- The increase in compressive strength after adding 0.5% fibers was 19.9 and 15.6% compared to the reference mixture after 7 and 28 days, respectively. This increase was 32.6 and 23.4% after 7 and 28 days, respectively, for 1% fibers, which is the optimal value of addition, but decreased by 16.7 and 26.8%, respectively, when the dose increased to 1.5%.

- The increase in splitting strength after the introduction of 0.5% fibers was 5.1 and 13% after 7 and 28 days, respectively. The respective increase when adding 1% fibers was 8.2 and 30.9% after 7 and 28 days, respectively, which was the optimal dose. When the fiber dose increased to 1.5%, the splitting strength decreased by 9 and 20.4% after 7 and 28 days, respectively, due to the low workability and low mixing water, leading to nonhomogeneity of the mixture.

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Optimizing Machine Learning Classifiers for Enhanced Cardiovascular Disease Prediction

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ABSTRACT

A key challenge in developing Machine Learning (ML) models for predicting or diagnosing Cardiovascular Disease (CVD), is selecting suitable algorithms and fine-tuning their parameters. In this study, we employed three ML techniques, namely Auto-WEKA, Decision Table/Naive Bayes (DTNB), and Multiobjective Evolutionary (MOE) fuzzy classifier to create diagnostic models using the Heart Disease Dataset from IEEE Dataport. Auto-WEKA generated a highly accurate model with a 100% success rate through optimal classifier selection and hyperparameter configuration. The DTNB classifier yielded a satisfactory 85.63% prediction accuracy concerning patients' risk levels. Further refinements, though, could help reduce possible misclassifications. Finally, the MOE fuzzy classifier achieved approximately 81.6% accuracy, indicating the potential for enhancing precision and recall values by adjusting classifier settings. Our findings underscore the promise of ML tools in CVD diagnosis and suggest further optimization of classifier parameters for superior performance.

Keywords-Machine Learning (ML); Auto-WEKA; Lazy IBK; DTNB; MOE fuzzy classifier; CVD

I. INTRODUCTION

As reported by the World Health Organization, Cardiovascular Disease (CVD) ranks as the primary death cause globally [1]. CVD occurs when the human heart struggles to function effectively and becomes incapable of supplying adequate blood to other bodily regions, therefore resulting in heart failure [2]. By facilitating early detection and professional prognosis, it is possible to reduce patient mortality rates. Several factors, such as medical history, age, gender, and lifestyle choices influence the prevalence of CVD. Adopting a healthy lifestyle can mitigate CVD risks by managing cholesterol levels and maintaining optimal blood pressure. Numerous studies have employed data mining techniques to identify methods which will reduce health risks and detect heart conditions quickly. The vast amount of data available in the healthcare sector allows these techniques to uncover previously unnoticed patterns and extract essential information that can support effective decision making. Data mining and machine-learning technologies are particularly valuable in healthcare due to their ability to analyze extensive volumes of data, ultimately yielding actionable insights [3-5]. However, diagnosing heart diseases quickly and accurately remains a significant challenge. Conventional diagnostic methods include blood tests, chest X-rays, and electrocardiograms (ECG). Recently, Machine Learning (ML) and artificial intelligence methods have emerged as critical contributors in the medical

field. Thus, various machine-learning and deep learning models can now be harnessed for disease diagnosis while offering classifications or outcome predictions. Furthermore, multiple studies have investigated the use of different ML models to categorize and predict CVD patients effectively. This study aims to meticulously examine and delineate the optimization of machine-learning classifiers for improving heart disease prediction accuracy through the evaluation of Auto-WEKA, DTNB, and MOE Fuzzy System performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Regarding heart disease prediction, numerous studies have utilized various ML methods for diagnostic purposes. For example, a previous study employed the ordinary learning method [5], which achieved an accuracy of approximately 98% using clinical data from the UCI standard Cleveland dataset. Other approaches have utilized the long short-term memory with symbolic aggregate approximation for ECG-based categorization [6], resulting in a 98.4% accuracy rate. Additionally, ML algorithms have been applied to identify key features that improve prediction accuracy [7] using a Support Vector Machine (SVM), with the obtained results showing an impressive accuracy rate of 91%. Alternative methods include the majority voting ensemble model [8], which demonstrated a 90% accuracy rate based on low-cost medical tests. The extreme learning machine algorithm has also been utilized [9]

to construct a diagnosis model, achieving an accuracy rate of approximately 80%. Moreover, the effective heart disease prediction system [10] displayed a 100% prediction rate engaging a neural network. Previous comparative studies [11] found that neural networks outperformed convolutional neural networks in terms of heart disease diagnosis in most instances. Improvements have been made by integrating naive Bayes classifiers with decision tables [12] and applying multiobjective evolutionary algorithms for fuzzy classification in different medical contexts [13]. In a more comprehensive study, various ML algorithms and deep learning techniques were implemented to analyze the UCI Heart Disease Dataset [14]. For instance, authors in [15] proposed a method that utilizes machine learning and enhanced auto categorical particle swarm optimization for early heart disease prediction, achieving 98% accuracy with logistic regression and SVMs on the Statlog and Cleveland datasets.

Selecting the appropriate algorithm and fine-tuning its parameters, constitutes a significant challenge in ML, often leading to suboptimal results due to improper decisions. The Auto-WEKA tool, integrated within the open-source WEKA package, addresses this issue by automating the process of algorithm selection and parameter adjustment for classification models. Auto-WEKA employs Bayesian optimization to map hyperparameters to algorithms, thereby enhancing their performance. Being compatible with any system that supports WEKA, Auto-WEKA operates similarly to other WEKA classifiers. It automatically identifies the optimal model and its parameters through Sequential Model-based Algorithm Configuration (SMAC) [16]. This method takes into consideration the noise in function evaluations and provides a reliable estimate of the best configuration performance [17].

The DTNB approach is a hybrid technique that leverages the strengths of both decision tables and naive Bayes classifiers. A decision table serves as a mechanism for constructing and utilizing a hybrid classifier. At each point during the search process, the DTNB algorithm assesses the benefit of dividing the dataset attributes into two disjoint subsets, one for the decision table and one for naive Bayes. A forward selection search technique is employed, in each step of which the selected attributes are modeled by naive Bayes and the remaining attributes are modeled by the decision table. It is important to note that all attributes are initially modeled by the decision table. In every step, the algorithm also considers the possibility of removing an attribute entirely from the model. The DTNB method strengths lie in its ability to capture complex relationships in the target data while maintaining simplicity. The decision table classifier is adept at handling complex interactions among attributes; however, it may suffer from overfitting when faced with a large number of irrelevant features. On the other hand, Naive Bayes classifiers perform well in high-dimensional spaces due to their attribute independence assumption. Nevertheless, they may be less effective when there are strong dependencies between attributes [12]. By combining the decision table and Naive Bayes classifiers, the DTNB method offers the following advantages over each individual method [12]:

- Improved accuracy. The hybrid DTNB method frequently produces better classification results by exploiting both complex attribute interactions and independent feature probabilities.
- Reduced overfitting. By considering both decision rules and feature independence, the model prevents sole reliance on complex interactions that may result in overfitting.
- Scalability. The DTNB method handles high-dimensional data efficiently because it exploits the advantages of both methods.

The construction of the fuzzy rule-based classifier is accomplished by employing the ENORA Multiobjective Evolutionary (MOE) algorithm within the multiobjective evolutionary fuzzy classifier. This process entails the optimization of two distinct objectives. The primary objective can be customized to either maximize accuracy, maximize the area under the ROC curve, or minimize the root mean squared error. Conversely, the secondary objective focuses on minimizing the number of fuzzy rules associated with the classifier. Ultimately, the non-dominated solutions in the final population exhibiting optimal fitness for the primary objective are selected as output [13]. This extensive body of research serves as a foundation for our investigation, through which we attempt to optimize the ML classifiers Auto-WEKA, DTNB, and evolutionary fuzzy systems to realize improved CVD prediction performance by providing a comprehensive performance assessment of these systems.

III. DATASET AND METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

In this study, we used the Heart Disease Dataset [15], which was obtained from IEEE Dataport. This dataset contains 12 input features, as shown in Table I.

B. Method

We present a method to classify cardiovascular patients by leveraging the dataset and employing the Auto-WEKA, DTNB, and MOE fuzzy classifiers. The proposed methodology comprises the following steps.

1. Data preprocessing. First, we acquire the CVD dataset and perform necessary preprocessing steps to ensure data consistency and quality. These procedures include error removal, handling missing values, encoding categorical variables, and data normalization or standardization.
2. Feature selection. We identify the most significant features for predicting CVDs in the dataset using various methods, e.g. correlation-based analysis, chi-squared tests, and mutual information, to determine the most impactful features for classification.
3. The Auto-WEKA classifier is trained on the training set. Auto-WEKA is an automated ML tool designed for classification tasks that iteratively selects suitable algorithms and hyperparameters.

4. The DTNB classifier is trained using the training set. This classifier combines the decision table and Naive Bayes algorithms to maintain sufficient accuracy while minimizing computational costs.
5. The MOE fuzzy classifier is trained on the training set to optimize accuracy, interpretability, and simplicity concurrently using genetic algorithms while incorporating fuzzy logic techniques in managing imprecision and uncertainty.

C. Model Evaluation

In order to evaluate the performance of the trained classifiers, various performance metrics are utilized on the test set. These key evaluation metrics comprise accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC) curve. To better understand these metrics, we will delve into their definitions, calculations, and potential relationships. TP, TN, FP, and FN denote True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives, and False Negatives, respectively.

- Accuracy measures the proportion of correct predictions out of the total number of predictions made. It is calculated as $(TP+TN)/(Total\ instances)$. However, when the data are imbalanced with uneven class distribution, accuracy may not be a reliable metric.
- Precision focuses on the ratio of TP to total predicted positives $(TP / (TP + FP))$. It essentially gauges how well a model can identify true positive instances while avoiding false positive instances.
- Also known as sensitivity or True Positive Rate (TPR), recall assesses the capability of a model to correctly identify positive cases from all actual positive cases. It is calculated as: $TP / (TP + FN)$.
- F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall that allows for a balance between both metrics making suitable to evaluate class imbalance scenarios where low prevalence rates are observed. It is defined as $2 \times ((Precision * Recall) / (Precision + Recall))$.
- The AUROC curve summarizes the performance of a classifier across all possible threshold levels by plotting the TPR against the False Positive Rate (FPR). Higher area under this curve, typically ranging from 0 to 1, indicates better classification performance.

Based on our analysis and the proposed methodology, we classified cardiovascular patients using Auto-WEKA, DTNB, and the MOE fuzzy classifiers. To ensure the highest accuracy and effective model selection, we implemented cross-validation methods or adjusted the dataset splits based on the obtained accuracy values. This approach allows for a rigorous evaluation and optimization of classifier performance, while mitigating concerns of overfitting related to specific training sets. By meticulously assessing the performance of each classifier—according to accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and AUROC curve—on different dataset splits or cross-validation folds, we are able to draw more reliable conclusions about the

performance of each classifier. This process aids in selecting the most appropriate method for CVD classification.

TABLE I. HEART DISEASE DATASET FEATURES

Feature	Feature discretion	Value range
age	Years	[29, 77]
sex	Sex	0 = female 1 = male
cp	Chest pain	0 = typical angina 1 = atypical angina 2 = nonangina pain 3 = asymptomatic
trestbps	Resting blood pressure (mmHg) on hospital admission	[94, 200]
chol	Serum cholesterol (mg/dl)	[126, 564]
fbs	Fasting blood sugar > 120 mg/dl	0 = false 1 = true
restecg	Resting electrocardiographic results	0 = normal 1 = ST-T wave abnormality 2 = left ventricular hypertrophy
thalach	Maximum heart rate	[71, 202]
exang	Exercise-induced angina	0 = no 1 = yes
oldpeak	ST depression induced by exercise relative to rest	[0, 6.2]
slope	Slope of the peak exercise ST segment	0 = up sloping 1 = flat 2 = down sloping
Target	Class	0: no 1: yes

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experiment 1

Auto-WEKA was utilized to optimize machine-learning algorithms and their respective hyperparameters. By leveraging the automated search process offered by WEKA's extensive toolkit, this experiment simplified the process of model selection and configuration, leading to highly accurate predictions and increased efficiency in handling complex data analysis tasks. In pursuit of unmatched performance, Experiment 1 rigorously assessed various algorithmic combinations. This approach allowed researchers to uncover insightful patterns and make well-informed decisions across numerous domains. The classifier was applied to the option values depicted in Figure 1. Detailed explanations of these options are provided in Table II. Auto-WEKA was directly implemented on the Heart Disease Dataset via the Auto-WEKA panel. This involved launching the tool on the dataset, which was used as the training set, in accordance with the option values outlined in Figure 1.

The results are presented in Table III. As can be observed, the Auto-WEKA tool selected lazy.IBk [18] as the best classifier. This model delivers an impressive accuracy of 100%, and a kappa statistic of 1, signifying flawless classifier performance [19]. Table VI provides a detailed breakdown of accuracy results by class, while Table VII exhibits the confusion matrix for the corresponding model. The remarkable performance of this model can be attributed to two primary factors: the selection of an appropriate classifier and the correct

setting of classifier hyperparameters, as evidenced by the values in Table II and Figure 1. Figure 2 depicts the ROC curve for the Auto-WEKA model, illustrating the model's performance in terms of the true positive rate versus the false positive rate.

TABLE II. AUTO-WEKA OPTIONS

seed	Seed for the random number generator
memLimit	Memory limit for runs (MB)
parallel runs	Number of runs to perform in parallel experiment
numDecimalPlaces	Number of decimal places in the output of numbers in the model
batchSize	Preferred number of instances to process if a batch prediction is performed. More or fewer instances may be provided, but this gives implementations a chance to specify a preferred batch size.
timeLimit	Time limit for tuning (minutes)
debug	If true, the classifier may output additional info to the console
best configs	How many best configurations should be returned as output
doNotCheckCapabilities	If set, classifier capabilities are not checked before the classifier is built (use with caution to reduce runtime)
metric	Target metric to optimize

Fig. 1. Auto-WEKA settings.

TABLE III. AUTO-WEKA CLASSIFIER OUTPUT

Best classifier	WEKA.classifier.lazy.IBK
Correctly classified instances	1190 (100%)
Incorrectly classified instances	0 (0%)
Kappa Statistic	1
Mean absolute error	0.03
Root mean squared error	0.06
Relative absolute error	0%
Root relative squared error	0%
Total number of instance	1190

TABLE IV. AUTO-WEKA ACCURACY BY CLASS

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F1-score	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
1	0.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	no
1	0.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	yes

TABLE V. AUTO WEKA CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual	Predicted		
	Output	Yes	No
	Yes	560	0
No	0	629	

Fig. 2. ROC curve for the Auto-WEKA model.

B. Experiment 2: DTNB Algorithm

In this experiment, we employed the DTNB algorithm from the WEKA software, following this scheme: weka.classifiers.rules.DTNB-X 1. The dataset was preprocessed to include only pertinent features such as age, chestpain type, resting bps, fasting blood sugar, resting ecg, and class. For feature selection, we used the cross-validation method (leave one out). In this context, we conducted a 10-fold stratified cross-validation to assess the classification model performance, therefore ensuring a constant distribution of classes for each fold. TABLE VI and Figure 3 illustrate the DTNB classifier options and settings, respectively.

TABLE VI. DTNB CLASSIFIER OPTIONS

numDecimalPlaces	Number of decimal places used for the output of numbers in the model.
batchSize	Preferred number of instances to process if batch prediction is performed. More or fewer instances may be provided, but this gives implementations a chance to specify a preferred batch size.
debug	If true, the classifier may output additional information to the console.
doNotCheckCapabilities	If set, classifier capabilities are not checked before the classifier is built (use with caution to reduce runtime).
evaluationMeasure	Measure used to evaluate the performance of attribute combinations used in the decision table.
search	Search method used to find good attribute combinations for the decision table.
displayRules	Sets whether rules are to be printed.
useIBk	Sets whether Simple instance-based learner that uses the class of the nearest k training instances(IBk)should be used rather than the majority class.
crossVal	Sets the number of folds for cross validation (1 = leave one out).
metric	Target metric to optimize

Fig. 3. DTNB settings.

We constructed the DTNB model in 0.24 s. It comprised 108 rules and covered all potential nonmatching instances by the majority class. Table VII presents the accuracy measurements during the cross-validation analysis, along with other significant evaluation metrics. Additionally, Table VIII provides detailed accuracy for each class and Table IX depicts the confusion matrix for the corresponding model. The area under the ROC curve of the DTNB model was found to be 0.9153, which highlights its efficacy in distinguishing between classes.

TABLE VII. DTBN CLASSIFIER OUTPUT

Correctly classified instances	1019 (85.63%)
Incorrectly classified instances	171 (14.36%)
Kappa statistic	0.7115
Mean absolute error	0.1849
Root mean squared error	0.1849
Relative absolute error	37.092%
Root relative squared error	68.511%
Total number of instance	1190

Fig. 4. ROC curve for the DTNB classifier.

TABLE VIII. TDBN ACCURACY BY CLASS

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
0.841	0.130	0.852	0.841	0.847	0.712	0.915	0.914	no
0.870	0.159	0.860	0.870	0.865	0.712	0.915	0.916	yes

TABLE IX. TDNB CLASSIFIER CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual	Predicted		
	Output	Yes	No
	Yes	472	89
No	82	547	

C. Experiment3: MultiObjective Evolutionary Fuzzy Classifier

In this experiment, we employed the MOE algorithm. The dataset was preprocessed to include only pertinent features such as age, chestpain type, resting bps, fasting blood sugar, resting ecg, and class. For feature selection, we used 10-fold stratified cross-validation to assess the performance of the classification model, thereby ensuring a constant distribution of classes for each fold. TABLE X and Figure 5 illustrate the MOE classifier options and settings, respectively.

TABLE X. MOE FUZZY CLASSIFIER OPTIONS

seed	Set the random seed.
maxRules	Set the value for the maximum number of rules (default: 10 + number of class labels).
minV	Set the value by which the domain of the variable is divided to obtain the minimum variance.
populationSize	Set the number of individuals in the population.
generations	Set the number of generations to evolve the population.
reportFrequency	Set the frequency to print the status of the evolutionary search.
numDecimalPlaces	Number of decimal places used in the output of numbers in the model.
batchSize	Preferred number of instances to process if batch prediction is being performed. More or fewer instances may be provided, but this gives implementations a chance to specify a preferred batch size.
logFile	Set the name for the log file.
maxSimilarity	Set the maximum similarity value for the fuzzy sets.
algorithm	Set the algorithm.
debug	If true, the classifier may output additional information to the console.
doNotCheckCapabilities	If set, classifier capabilities are not checked before the classifier is built (use with caution to reduce runtime).
evaluationMeasure	Set the evaluation criteria.
maxV	Set the value by which the domain of the variable is divided to obtain the maximum variance.
maxLabels	Set the value of maximum number of labels.

TABLE XI. OUTPUT OF MULTIOBJECTIVE EVOLUTIONARY FUZZY CLASSIFIER.

Correctly classified instances	972 (81.6807 %)
Incorrectly classified instances	218 (18.3193 %)
Kappa statistic	0.6307
Mean absolute error	0.2374
Root mean squared error	0.428
Relative absolute error	36.7584
Root relative squared error	85.742
Total number of instance	1190

Table XI presents the accuracy measurements during the cross-validation analysis along with other significant evaluation metrics. Additionally, Table XII provides detailed accuracy for each class, and Table XIII presents the confusion matrix for the corresponding model. The area under the ROC curve of the MOE model was found to be 0.8139.

TABLE XII. DETAILED ACCURACY RESULTS FOR THE MULTI-OBJECTIVE EVOLUTIONARY FUZZY CLASSIFIER

TPR	FPR	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
0.763	0.135	0.834	0.763	0.797	0.633	0.814	0.7480	no
0.865	0.237	0.804	0.865	0.833	0.633	0.814	0.766	yes

Fig. 5. ROC curve for MOE fuzzy classifier.

TABLE XIII. MOE FUZZY CLASSIFIER CONFUSION MATRIX

Actual	Predicted		
	Output	Yes	No
	Yes	428	133
No	85	455	

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we utilized three machine learning tools: Auto-WEKA, DTNB, and the MOE fuzzy classifier. These tools were used to construct diagnostic models for heart disease, employing the Heart Disease Dataset from IEEE Dataport. The Auto-WEKA tool automatically identifies the most suitable model and optimizes parameter settings for classification or regression tasks. In addition, we also investigated the hybrid DTNB and MOE fuzzy classifiers to achieve optimal performance.

Our findings suggest that the Auto-WEKA tool was effectively utilized to construct a highly accurate model, with lazy.IBk emerging as the best classifier. This model achieved an impressive accuracy rate of 100%. This success can be primarily attributed to the efficient selection of classifiers and the appropriate configuration of hyperparameters. Our study also revealed that the DTNB classifier developed a model with an accuracy of approximately 85.63% in predicting patients' risk levels based on their medical records. This demonstrates satisfactory performance in making reliable predictions. However, further enhancements may be necessary to reduce misclassification instances.

Finally, the MOE fuzzy classifier attained an overall accuracy of approximately 81.6%. Although this classifier

made satisfactory distinctions among patient classes, there is still potential for improvement in the precision and recall results. Future studies could explore this potential by adjusting various classifier settings, such as the population size and the number of generations. Table XIV offers a comparison between the outcomes derived from default settings and those achieved after fine-tuning the classifier's hyperparameters. It becomes clear that the precise configuration of these settings leads to an enhancement of the overall results.

To contextualize our findings with other studies that have adopted machine learning methods for heart disease prediction, our work demonstrates varying degrees of success in comparison with alternative approaches. These include ordinary learning methods [5], long short-term memory with symbolic aggregate approximation [6], support vector machines [7], majority voting ensemble models [8], extreme learning machine algorithms [9], effective heart disease prediction systems [10], and neural networks [14]. Notable accomplishments from these studies encompass accuracy rates ranging between 80% and 100%. This underscores the effectiveness of machine learning tools in aiding heart disease diagnosis using standard datasets.

In conclusion, our study's findings underscore the effectiveness of machine learning tools in facilitating heart disease diagnosis through standard datasets. However, optimizing performance may require fine-tuning critical classifier parameters to yield more precise results, thereby opening avenues for future research. This study adds to the burgeoning body of research on the application of machine learning techniques in medical diagnosis and introduces innovative approaches to optimize heart disease diagnostic models

TABLE XIV. RESULT COMPARISON FOR DEFAULT AND ADJUSTED PARAMETER SETTINGS

Classifier	MOE Fuzzy		TDBN		AUTO-WEKA	
	Default setting Accuracy	Adjusted setting Accuracy	Default setting Accuracy	Adjusted setting Accuracy	Default setting Accuracy	Adjusted setting Accuracy
Correctly classified instances	76.2%	81.6%	79.5%	85.6%	90.5%	100%
Incorrectly classified instances	3.73%	18.3%	20.4%	14.3%	9.41%	0%
Kappa statistic	0.52	0.63	0.58	0.71	0.81	1
Mean absolute error	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.18	0.09	0.03
Root mean squared error	0.48	0.428	0.40	0.18	0.30	0.06

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The Impact of Injection/Pumping Wells on the Pollution Transport in Groundwater

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ABSTRACT

The natural quality of groundwater tends to be degraded by industry, agriculture, and wastewaters. There are several alternatives to prevent migration and the spread of pollution in groundwater. Some alternatives are physical such as grouting, or slurry walls. Others could be hydrodynamic containment by injection or pumping wells. Injection wells are used to confine a pollutant in place or dilute its concentration by injecting clean water into the aquifer. Pumping wells are used to discharge the pollutant out of the groundwater reservoir or act as interceptors. In this research, the hydraulic characteristics and behavior of the hydrodynamic methods are investigated by using numerical simulation. In this investigation, the numerical model MT3D has been integrally used with the flow model MODFLOW. Injection/pumping rate, screen length and layer, and the number of wells are considered. The results have shown that increasing the rate or the number of the injection/pumping wells permits less pollution spread. Changing the screen length of the injection/pumping wells are not effective in preventing the pollution spread in the long-term. Changing the number of wells has more effect on a containment spread. Injection wells can prevent the spread of contaminants more than pumping wells.

Keywords-groundwater; pollution transport; injection wells; pumping wells; MT3D model; MODFLOW model

I. INTRODUCTION

Groundwater supply is considered a vital aspect of human wellbeing. Groundwater provides the population with water for drinking and irrigation. The sustainability of groundwater

quality and management is highly challenged in this regard [1-16]. Hydrodynamic control for containing contaminants in place by injection wells or removing them from the ground by discharge wells are considered effective methods to prevent

contamination spread in a hydrogeological system [17-24]. With pumping, there is always the problem of what to do with the contaminated water removed from the ground. On site treatment is required before injecting the water to the subsurface or releasing it to surface water bodies [25-26]. Injection wells could be used to dilute the groundwater pollution by the injection of clean water or as interceptors for diverting the flow direction. The number of injection or withdrawal wells and the pumping/injection rates can be minimized through the proper choice of well location and distance between wells [27-28]. This could be achieved through good understanding of the problem and implementing successful design for the controlling system in each specific site. In this paper, investigation of injection and pumping wells is performed and discussed. The numerical models MT3D and MODFLOW are employed. Change of injection/pumping rate, depth and position of the screen, and distribution of wells around the pollution source are considered.

II. MODEL DESCRIPTION

The study is implemented by using the transport model (MT3D) through the flow model (MODFLOW). MT3D is a computer model for the two or three dimensional simulation of advection, dispersion, and chemical reactions of contaminants in groundwater flow systems [29]. A mixed Eulerian-Lagrangian approach is used by the MT3D model to solve the advective-dispersive-reactive equation. This can be done depending on the supposition that concentration changes cannot influence the flow field significantly [30]. The model uses a modular structure like that implemented in the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) modular three-dimensional finite-difference groundwater flow model, referred to as MODFLOW [31-33]. MT3D retrieves the hydraulic heads and the various flow and sink/source terms saved by MODFLOW, combining the hydraulic boundary conditions [34-35]. The structure of MT3D can readily simulate the terms of advection, dispersion, and source or sink mixing of chemical reactions. Further, MT3D can simulate the concentration changes for one kind of contaminant considering the hydrological and chemical reactions with different kinds of boundary conditions and extrinsic sources or sinks. The MT3D model includes the chemical reactions. These reactions are controlled linearly or nonlinearly of sorption and first-order biodegradation [36]. MT3D fits the spatial discretization and boundary conditions as: (1) confined/unconfined aquifer layers, (2) sloped model layers and cell thickness within the same layer, (3) one kind of mass concentration or flow of mass through boundaries, and (4) the effects of solute transport of extrinsic sources or sinks like springs, wells, ditches, rivers, recharge, and evapotranspiration. The MT3D model, like the MODFLOW, consists of a main program and subroutines, called modules, which are grouped into a series of "packages".

The hydraulic heads and fluxes at each time step are solved by the MODFLOW model and used by MT3D model. Prior to entering the stress period loop, the program executes three procedures. First, the simulation problem is defined by identifying the model size and the number of stress periods, and specifying the various transport options to be used in the simulation. Computer memory is allocated for the data arrays

whose dimensions depend on the parameters specified in the Define procedure. A second step is reading and preparing the input data which are constant within the current stress period. The transport model obtains the location, type, and flow rates of all sources and sinks simulated in the flow model. Then, a third procedure reads and processes the hydraulic heads and flow terms saved by the flow model, and the specified hydrologic boundary conditions. The transport step loop contains four procedures. The Advance procedure determines an appropriate step size for use in the current transport step. The Solve procedure solves each transport component with an explicit mixed Eulerian-Lagrangian solution scheme and calculates the mass into or out of the aquifer through each component. The Budget procedure estimates the global mass balance information and gets the printouts and saved simulation results as needed according to the control options of the user-specified output. The equation of solute transport in a porous medium is a partial differential one [37-40]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (D_{ij} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (C V_i) + \frac{q_s}{n} (C - C_s) + \sum_{k=1}^N R_k = \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

$$V_i = -\frac{K_{ij}}{n} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x_j} \quad (2)$$

where i, j are the Cartesian coordinate directions, $C = C(x, y, t)$ is the pollutant concentration [$M.L^{-3}$], $V_i = V_i(x, y, t)$ is the seepage or average pore water velocity in the X_i [$L.T^{-1}$] direction, $D_{ij} = D_{ij}(x, y, t)$ is the dispersion coefficient tensor [$L^2.T^{-1}$], $n = n\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)$ is the effective porosity,

$K_{ij} = K_{ij}\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)$ is the hydraulic conductivity tensor [$L.T^{-1}$], q_s is the volumetric flux per unit volume representing sources (positive) and sinks (negatives) [T^{-1}], C_s is the concentration of the sources/sinks [$M.L^{-3}$], X_i represents the Cartesian coordinates, t is the time [T], and $\sum_{k=1}^N R_k$ is the adsorption and decay by chemical reaction terms [$M.L^{-3}.T^{-1}$]. The components of the tensor D_{ij} in a system of three-dimensional Cartesian coordinates are obtained through the transformation of coordinates formula:

$$D_{xx} = \alpha_L \frac{V_y^2}{|V|} + \alpha_T \frac{V_x^2}{|V|} + \alpha_T \frac{V_z^2}{|V|} \quad (3)$$

$$D_{yy} = \alpha_L \frac{V_x^2}{|V|} + \alpha_T \frac{V_y^2}{|V|} + \alpha_T \frac{V_z^2}{|V|} \quad (4)$$

$$D_{zz} = \alpha_L \frac{V_z^2}{|V|} + \alpha_T \frac{V_x^2}{|V|} + \alpha_T \frac{V_y^2}{|V|} \quad (5)$$

$$D_{xy} = D_{yx} = (\alpha_L - \alpha_T) \frac{V_x V_y}{|V|} \quad (6)$$

$$D_{xz} = D_{zx} = (\alpha_L - \alpha_T) \frac{V_x V_z}{|V|} \quad (7)$$

$$D_{yz} = D_{zy} = (\alpha_L - \alpha_T) \frac{V_y V_z}{|V|} \quad (8)$$

where α_L is the longitudinal dispersivity [L], α_T is the transverse dispersivity [L], and $|V| = (V_x^2 + V_y^2 + V_z^2)^{1/2}$, V_x , V_y and V_z are the components of the velocity vector along x, y and z axes.

III. THE HYPOTHETICAL ZONE OF STUDY

The hypothetical zone of study is square in shape with dimensions 800 m by 800 m. It has been divided into a grid of 10,000 cells (100×100). The studied region covers a phreatic aquifer with a total depth of 30 m. The aquifer is assumed to have four layers. The thickness of the layers in the downward direction is 5, 5, 10, and 10 m. Thus, the total number of cells in the simulated problem amounts to 40,000. Each layer is homogeneous and isotropic with a hydraulic conductivity of 10 m/day and porosity 0.3. Dispersivity is taken as 500 m without considering sorption and decay. Groundwater flow takes place from the left to the right boundaries under the effect of the specified head boundaries with values of 29 and 26 m. A pollution source is assumed in the aquifer at the intersection cell of row 41 and column 24. The source has a concentration of 300 PPM. Figure 1 represents a plan view and a longitudinal section A-A showing the corresponding equipotential heads and velocity vectors.

Fig. 1. (a) Equipotential lines and velocity vectors of the study zone, (b) a cross section A-A showing the equipotential lines with the velocity.

IV. INJECTION WELLS

Injection wells have been studied considering the effect of injection rate, screen length, and number of wells on a contaminant spread.

A. Injection Rate

Four injection wells around the pollution source feeding clean water into the groundwater reservoir are assumed. The wells' screen is fully penetrating the four layers of the aquifer.

The injection rate is taken as 600 m³/day from each well. The resulting equipotential lines and the concentration lines are presented in Figure 2. It is shown that the pollution spread is contained in a limited zone between the wells due to the clean water injected by the four surrounding wells. The diameter of the spread circle is about 100 m. When the injection rate is reduced to 300 m³/day, more spread of the pollution takes place in the aquifer, as shown in Figure 3. The diameter of the resulting spread zone around the pollution source increases to about 300m.

Fig. 2. Plan view of the concentration lines when having four injection wells of clean water with a rate of 600 m³/day.

Fig. 3. Plan view of concentration lines when having four injection wells of clean water with a rate of 300 m³/day.

B. Screen Well Depth

The case of having wells with an injection rate of 300 m³/day has been repeated with a screen length of only 10 m penetrating the lowest layer of the aquifer. Figure 4 shows the results in the form of equi-concentration lines of the pollutant, in the first layer. A slight increase in the concentration can be noticed when comparing the results with the ones shown in Figure 3. This slight increase is related to having the injection screen away in the fourth layer.

Fig. 4. Plan view of concentration lines when having four injection wells of clean water with a rate of 300 m³/day and screen in the lower 10 m of the well.

C. Well Number

When the number of the injection wells was reduced to two upstream, more pollution spread took place downstream the contaminant source as shown in Figure 5. The increase of the pollution zone is noticed when it is compared with the corresponding one in Figure 3 that has the same conditions but with four injection wells.

Fig. 5. Plan view of concentration lines when having two injection wells of clean water with a rate of 300 m³/day.

V. PUMPING WELLS AS INTERCEPTORS

Investigation of hydraulics of contaminant withdrawal by pumping wells as interceptors is performed and discussed in this section. The studied hydraulic characteristics include pumping rate, depth, and number of wells.

A. Pumping Rate

Four pumping wells are assumed around the pollution source to keep the contaminant in place and prevent its spread through the aquifer. The wells are assumed to have screens which fully penetrate the aquifer with a pumping rate of 600 m³/day. The resulting equipotential lines and the equi-

concentration lines in PPM are presented in Figure 6. It is shown that the polluted zone is contained between the four wells. When the pumping rate is reduced to 300 m³/day, the wells are not capable anymore of preventing the spread of the pollution zone which has extended outside the wells, as shown in Figure 7. A similar result was found but when increasing the time transport for reducing the pumping rate in [41].

Fig. 6. Plan view of concentration lines when having four pumping wells with a rate of 600 m³/day.

Fig. 7. Plan view of concentration lines when having four pumping wells with a rate of 300 m³/day.

B. Screen Well Depth

The case of having wells with a pumping rate of 300 m³/day was repeated with a screen length of 10 m that penetrates only the lower part of the aquifer. The corresponding concentration in the first layer is shown in Figure 8 showing more pollution compared with the results of the fully penetrating wells shown in Figure 7. This takes place in the first layer because the discharging screen is far in the lowest (fourth) layer.

C. Well Number

The number of discharging wells is reduced to two downstream as in Figure 9 and then to one as in Figure 10. The results show an increase in the pollution spread in comparison with the results shown in Figure 7.

Fig. 8. Plan view of concentration lines when having four pumping wells with a rate of $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ and screen in the lower 10 m of the well.

Fig. 9. Plan view of concentration lines when having two downstream pumping wells with a rate of $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$.

Fig. 10. Plan view of concentration lines when having one downstream pumping well with a rate of $300 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$.

VI. IMPACT INTERRELATIONSHIP AMONG INJECTION AND PUMPING WELLS

Figure 11 shows the interrelationship of the impacts among injection and pumping wells according to the flow rate, well screen length, and well number. The base run for

injection/pumping wells is indicated in blue/green colors. Figure 11 shows that the injection wells can prevent the spread of contamination more than the pumping wells. Full screen length is a good choice for decreasing the contamination for injection/pumping wells. Increasing the injection/pumping well number prevents more the contamination spread.

Fig. 11. Interrelationship of the impacts among injection and pumping wells.

VII. CONCLUSION

The current study helps understanding the hydraulic behavior of hydrodynamic containment of a contaminant in groundwater in order to achieve successful design of controlling systems. The main findings of the study include the following points:

- Hydrodynamic control of the pollution spread with the use of injection or pumping wells is an effective method.
- Decreasing the rate or the number of the injection/pumping wells permits more pollution spread.
- Changing the screen length of the injection well is not effective in preventing the pollution spread on the long-term.
- The effect of changing the screen length on the pollution spread is more in the case of pumping wells than in injection wells.
- Changing the number of the injection/pumping wells effects the contaminant spread.

The present investigation draws the decision makers' attention to the main factors that should be considered in the design of real applications. The injection/pumping rates as well as the number of wells should be studied well in each specific site in order to design a successful hydrodynamic system.

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GPU Shader Analysis and Power Optimization Model

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid advancements in 3D game technology, workload characterization has become crucial for each new generation of games. The increased complexity of scenes in 3D games allows for stunning real-time visual quality. However, handling such workloads results in significant power consumption over the GPU rendering pipeline. The focus of the current paper is low power optimization, targeting texture memory, geometry engine, pixel, and rasterization, as these components are significant contributors to the power consumption of a typical GPU. The proposed methodology integrates the Dynamic Voltage Frequency Scaling (DVFS) technique, adjusting voltage and frequency based on the workload analysis of frame rates with respect to the scenes of 3D games. Frame rates of 60 fps and 30 fps are set up to understand and manage the workload on frames. Furthermore, for comparative analysis, various frame-level power analysis schemes such as No DVFS implemented, Frame History Method, Frame Signature Method, and Tiled History-based are introduced. The proposed scheme consistently surpasses these frame-level schemes, with fewer missed deadlines, while having the lowest energy consumption per frame rate. The implementation resulted in a remarkable 65% improvement in quality, indicated by a reduction in deadline misses, along with a substantial 60% energy saving.

Keywords-3D scene rendering pipeline; frames; GPU; DVFS; geometry; pixel; texture; workload

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current landscape of multimedia devices and applications, 3D models have gained widespread usage, particularly in high-definition video games, which constitute to be a major part of computer graphics. In the latest Top 500 supercomputer rankings, 101 of these supercomputers are powered by GPUs for acceleration [1]. There are many 3D model applications that exhibit compelling variations in the workload in the sequence of frames. Some high intensity workloads of 3D models [2] do not suite graphics design to achieve better performance and time. The goal is to identify opportunities for optimizing power consumption without compromising visual quality and user experience. An algorithm based on Dynamic Voltage Frequency Scaling (DVFS) [3, 4], is implemented to explore the characteristics confined to frame controlled rendering GPUs and reach desirable power savings. The workload of each frame is analyzed in the 3D scene by considering factors such as geometry [5, 6], textures, pixels [7], and rasterization. This analysis helps in understanding computational intensity of each frame. Matrix computing operations are commonly regarded as the cornerstone of various computations in the field of scientific applications.

As the digital world continues to expand, its environmental impact, sustainability, cost savings, scalability, battery life, and heat dissipation are major power consumption issues that have to be addressed. The experimental findings in similar works [8, 9] show decrease in energy consumed by GPUs up to 20%. The trade-offs between performance and power consumption in GPUs involve a delicate balance, and designers must make strategic decisions to optimize both aspects. Higher clock frequencies generally lead to better performance. But higher clock frequencies often require higher voltage levels, resulting in increased power consumption [3, 4, 10]. To enhance both speed and the quality of rendering, while considering the significance of textures and geometry, cutting-edge, high-performance texture streaming systems have been developed [11, 12]. The power consumption in shaders is influenced by a combination of factors related to the complexity of the shader code, the number of shader invocations, and memory access patterns. Geometric complexity increases the number of vertices and brings a series of operations in the vertex shader with transformations and lighting calculations, leading to higher power consumption. High-resolution textures or frequent sampling can increase memory and bandwidth usage, contributing to higher power consumption. Sophisticated visual effects also contribute towards more power consumption.

These data are utilized for predicting the workload for the frames [13]. At the onset of the decoding process, buffering is applied to each frame comprising of GoP (Group of Pictures) and the workload estimation is calculated for the buffered frames. Minimal value relating frequency-voltage during the decoded period for meeting the deadlines for GoPs is noted in [14]. Figure 1 exhibits the varying processing time of successive frames in the following games: Cyberpunk 2077, Assassin's Creed Valhalla, Cow Boy Simulator, Tomb Raider, Forsaken World. It is observed from the graph that the workload on the frames 10-15 is much lower compared with the workload of frames in the range of 1-7. Considering this major gap with respect to workload variations, considerable power savings can be achieved by adjusting the computational capability of GPUs based on workload variation in frames.

Fig. 1. Workload variation observed in the games.

II. METHODOLOGY

The architectural design of the proposed methodology is based on the input of the 3D scene specific to game applications and is depicted in Figure 2. The implemented architecture primarily comprises four key components:

- Video encoding and decoding for the frame rate analysis of the scenes.
- Workload characterization on parameter geometry, pixel, texture, and raster.
- Graphics Rendering Parameters Control (GRPC), which serves as a functionality that changes the parameters to influence the power consumed during runtime.
- The DVFS technique is responsible for managing the core frequencies of GPU.

In the initial stage, GPU's power consumption and connected resources used under rendering of the 3D scene are examined. To achieve continuous parallelism and placement on the device, the libraries of TensorFlow are used. Power consuming parameters include: geometric complexity, texture memory, pixelization, and textures workload. The key strategies include DVFS and frame rate analysis based on workload. The computation of workload considers the parameters for every frame rendered in a 3D game scene. Utilizing these frame workloads as a basis, DVFS method is implemented, involving adjustments to both GPU voltage and frequency. The frequency threshold is established ranging from a minimum of 30 to a maximum of 60 frames per second (fps). If the current framerate is below the target framerate, the frequency is augmented. Conversely, if the current framerate

surpasses the target, the frequency is diminished to attain optimal power savings. Examining the present load status of the GPU, which furnishes details regarding its idle intervals and workload distribution, enables the reduction of power consumption through the fine-tuning of frequency-voltage variations on the dedicated GPUs.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the proposed methodology.

The workload of a scene from a 3D model refers to the computational effort or processing requirements needed to render and display that scene on a computer or GPU. Finally, after careful analysis of the workloads observed on each frame, four parameters, namely geometry workload, pixel workload, texture workload, and rasterization workload contribute in possessing the workload for each frame of the rendered scene along with their major contribution in power consumption. The geometry workload on scenes refers to the computational effort and processing requirements related to the geometric aspects of a 3D scene during rendering. The total count in vertex shader instructions (Wv) under each frame can be calculated by:

$$Wv = V \times Nv \quad (1)$$

where Nv is the total length of instructions for each vertex shader program, and V represents the vertices total count for each frame. The geometry stage workload is mainly determined by the number of vertices processed by the shader program multiplied by the instruction length. The equation for Geometry workload (Wg) as a combination of workload on the vertex shader (Wv) and the workload observed due to clipping and binning, which is considered to be proportional to the count of primitives (P) is defined as:

$$Wg = Wv + P = V \times Nv + P \quad (2)$$

Pixel shading is a fundamental aspect of determining the final appearance of objects in the rendered image. The measure of workload identified due to pixel shading (Wp) is expressed as:

$$Wp = A \times Np \quad (3)$$

where Np depicts the pixel shader program length, indicating the amount of computations required for each pixel. The texture workload measure Wt can be estimated by considering the texels count that are read for every pixel under examination. The workload on texture can be expressed by:

$$Wt = A \times M \times t \quad (4)$$

where A represents the texels count on each pixel, capturing the workload due to basic texture access, M represents the number of textures associated with each pixel, considering scenarios where multiple textures are used for blending or multi-texturing effects, and t represents the number of texel samples required for filtering. Enabling early z-test in our experiments reveals that around 50% of the pixels are ignored at this particular stage, leading to a significant reduction in both pixel shading and texturing workloads. Hence, with early z enabled:

$$Wp = 0.5 \times A \times Np \text{ and } Wt = 0.5 \times A \times M \times t \quad (5)$$

Operations on rasters, including depth-stencil testing and color blending, primarily contribute to frame buffer memory's bandwidth. For R raster operations in each primitive, every pixel for primitives require $2 \times R$ rate of access towards buffers of frame. The respective operations are included with the sum of reading and writing from and to the memory of the frame buffer, hence the factor of 2 is considered. Hence, raster operations workload (Wr) is characterized by:

$$Wr = A \times 2 \times R \quad (6)$$

During workload analysis for the parameter texturing, rasterization and pixel shading operations are executed parallelly, so the processing speed is determined through the slowest parameter executed. Hence, correlative increment in the workload is found from the increment in any one of these parameters. From Figure 3, we see that the proposed methodology has almost ignorable under prediction count compared to the frame oriented signature-based scheme. Function `tf.debugging.set_log_device_placement` checks out the device placement. The `tf.function` and `input_pipeline_analyzer` display descriptive GPU core analysis results, including GPU's step-time and duration of GPU time spent. TensorFlow Stats exhibits the performance for each TensorFlow op, executed on the device. Nvidia management tool NVML is employed for monitoring the power consumption in the graphics card.

Fig. 3. Accuracy of the proposed method predictions.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND IMPLEMENTATION

NVIDIA Nsight [15] is a powerful profiling tool providing in-depth analysis of GPU performance and frame rates. The frames of six 3D games are considered: Cyberpunk (CP) provides an excellent benchmark for testing frame rates and performance on high-end systems. Assassin's Creed Valhalla (AC) depicts the workload characterized on each frame. Cow Boy simulator (CB) possess intense action sequences, making

it ideal for frame analysis. Tomb Raider (TR) features complex lighting, shadows, and detailed textures that stress the rendering pipeline. Forsaken World (FW) and Mudness offroad Car simulator (MC) are great for analyzing GPU performance under heavy rendering loads. Deadline misses, achieved frame rates, and normalized energy consumption at 30 and 60 fps are analyzed for various frame level power analysis schemes. In the suggested approach, we assess frame correlation by comparing the geometric workload of the current frame to a previous frame. If the workloads of the frames are similar, we consider previous frame's workload as a reliable estimate of the existing current frame. In our experiments, we set empirically the threshold for geometry workload to 10%. After completing the geometry processing, we analyzed other three frame components to determine the optimal processing frequency. Based on the workload analysis, the frames are divided into two categories:

- Light Frames: Frames with an estimated workload that is equal to or less than previous frame's workload.

$$W(fi) \leq W(fi-1) \quad (8)$$

Suppose the current frame rate surpasses 60 fps. Within this range we systematically decrease the core frequency of the GPU. This sequence ensures that the workload is effectively managed with the minimal consumption of resources and power. Consequently, if the frame rate drops below the lower limit of 30 fps, the GPU core's frequency level is increased to enhance the frame rate.

- Heavy Frames: Frames with an anticipated workload that surpasses previous frame's workload:

$$W(fi) > W(fi-1) \quad (9)$$

In the second scenario, we focus on the workload of the present frame. To handle this augmented workload, we operate at the maximum available frequency.

The frame workload Algorithm using DVFS is presented below.

Algorithm 1: Proposed frame workload-based DVFS method

Step 1: Initialization: Set initial values for fps and corresponding voltage and frequency levels

$Min = 30$ fps, $Max = 60$ fps and standard voltage and frequency levels

Step 2: Frame and workload analysis of the current frame. Calculate geometry workload, pixel workload, raster operations workload, and texture workload from (2), (3), (4), and (6).

Step 3: Frame workload classification: $low \leq 30$ fps, $medium = 45$ fps, $high >= 60$ fps.

Step 4: Voltage and Frequency Adjustment: If the current frame workload \leq previous frame workload decrease frequency levels. Else increase frequency levels.

Step 5: Frame processing: Process current frame using adjusted V and f levels to conserve power.

Step 6: Performance evaluation: Compare the achieved performance with the desired target set. Assess whether the performance is meeting the desired criteria or further adjustments is needed.

Step 7: Repeat steps 1 to 6 for subsequent frames in the sequence

Step 8: End the algorithm when all the frames have been processed.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For experimentation, the results are generated for GPU processors compatible with 3, 6, 9, and 12 levels of frequency and voltage, providing options in adjustments over DVFS. Results are produced for frame rates with thresholds of 30 fps and 60 fps, enabling us to evaluate performance and efficiency in two contexts: (i) slack utilization for lighter frame rates and (ii) guaranteeing the capability to attain deadlines for higher frame rates. In Figure 4, we can observe comparative percentages of deadline misses for the No DVFS implemented (WD) method, Frame History Method (FHM), Frame Signature Method (FSM), Tiled History-based Method (THM), and our Proposed Method (PM), for the CP game at a target frame rate of 60 fps. Notably, the FHM DVFS scheme exhibits the highest number of deadline misses. The FSM performs better compared to FHM but still results in notable deadline misses. The PM excels due to its ability to implement early corrective measures, leading to reduction in the number of under-predictions. Comparing 3-level and 2-level DVFS schemes, it is observed that the 3-level scheme results into deadline misses. The 2-level scheme opts F_{max} frequency to prevent deadline misses, but this decision might lead to some slack under-utilization. The proposed methodology in turn exhibits superior efficiency in handling both scenarios effectively.

Figure 5 illustrates the impact of deadline misses. In the proposed methodology we can reach a frame rate that closely reflects the predictive frame rate, meanwhile the frame-based DVFS technique undergoes notable decrease in the frame rate. Referring towards Table I, history-based schemes lead to a drop of up to 10 fps, but the PM experiences maximum drop around 1 fps. Most often, required predictive frequency F underlies among two levels, F_1 and F_2 ($F_1 < F < F_2$). As a result, the frame is processed at F_2 to meet the timing constraints. Similarly, in the History and Signature Method schemes, the frame with the average frequency nearer to F can be reached alternating between frequencies F_1 and F_2 for time durations t_1 and t_2 such that:

$$F_1 \times t_1 + F_2 \times t_2 = F \times TD, t_1 + t_2 = TD$$

In our experiments, we found that using this approach resulted in more than 40% of the frames missing their deadlines.

However, in the proposed DVFS scheme, we can effectively utilize the slack obtained from processing a frame at F_2 to slow down future frames, allowing us to process the frame at an average frequency closer to the desired F . This is observed through the results achieved with respect to frames at 60 fps, as in Figure 6. But, for the processed frames at 30 fps,

as in Figure 7, we conclude that the PM consumes a bit more power compared to the legacy history-based schemes. To attain proper understanding of the comparison with respect to power efficiency introduced in each scheme, Normalized Energy per Normalized Frame Rate is evaluated. From the results examined in Figure 8, it is observed that the Energy per Frame Rate is minimized under the implemented frame-based DVFS scheme which outperforms frame history and signature DVFS techniques in terms of energy efficiency. The results for the remaining applications and various frame rate per second requirements, at 60 fps, are provided in Figures 9-11.

Fig. 4. Deadline misses at the desired frame rate of 60 fps.

Fig. 5. Achieved frame rate at the desired target of 60 fps.

Fig. 6. Normalized energy consumption at a frame rate of 60 fps.

Fig. 7. Normalized energy consumption at a frame rate of 30 fps.

Fig. 8. Energy consumption per frame rate when operating at 30 fps.

Deadline Misses													
(3 Levels)						(6 Levels)							
	CP	AC	CB	TR	FW	MC		CP	AC	CB	TR	FW	MC
WD	0	1	2	3	4	4.8	WD	0	1	2	3	4	4.8
FHM	10	8	10	11	10	10.5	FHM	13	9	15	17	18	18.5
FSM	7	8	9	10	11	11.6	FSM	8	8	12	12	13	13.5
THM	2	3	6	8	10	10.5	THM	2	4	6	8	9	11
PM	0	2	3	3.8	4	5	PM	0	2	3	4	4	5
(9 Levels)						(12 Levels)							
WD	0	1	2	3	4	4.8	WD	0	1	2	3.2	4.5	5
FHM	20	17	19	22	23	25	FHM	21	18	19.3	22.4	24	27
FSM	10	11	12	14	14	15	FSM	11	11	13	15	16	18
THM	2	7	8	11	13	10	THM	3	8	9	12	14	12
PM	0	2	3	4	4	5	PM	0	3	4	4.5	5	5.7

Fig. 9. DVFS results at 60 fps, regarding deadline misses.

Frame Rate													
(3 Levels)						(6 Levels)							
	CP	AC	CB	TR	FW	MC		CP	AC	CB	TR	FW	MC
WD	50	54	55	56	58	59	WD	50	54	55	56	58	59
FHM	42	45	42	47	50	52	FHM	40	42	40	45	48	50
FSM	45	45	46	47	48	49	FSM	45	45	45.5	46	46	47
THM	48	50	48	48	49	49.5	THM	48	50	48	48	49	49.5
PM	50	51	51.5	52	52.4	53	PM	50	51	51.5	52	52.4	53
(9 Levels)						(12 Levels)							
WD	50	54	55	56	58	59	WD	50	54	55	56	58	59
FHM	36	40	46	22	23	21	FHM	36	40	46	22	23	21
FSM	40	43	42	42	43	42	FSM	40	43	42	42	43	42
THM	46	48	49	49	50	50	THM	46	48	49	49	50	50
PM	48	48	49	49	51	51	PM	48	48	49	49	51	51

Fig. 10. DVFS results at 60 fps, regarding framerates.

V. CONCLUSION

Following a thorough examination, we identified the vertex processing, texture operations, geometry engine, and rasterization as significant factors influencing the power consumption of a typical GPU. The comparative outcomes of the proposed approach, in relation to both history-based and signature-based methods, demonstrate notable power conservation.

Normalized Energy/ Frame Rate													
(3 Levels)						(6 Levels)							
	CP	AC	CB	TR	FW	MC		CP	AC	CB	TR	FW	MC
WD	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.03	WD	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.03
FHM	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.03	1.03	FHM	0.45	1.00	1.03	1.03	1.04	1.04
FSM	0.30	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	1.03	FSM	0.42	1.03	1.05	1.06	1.06	1.08
THM	0.28	0.80	0.82	0.90	0.92	0.95	THM	0.43	0.90	0.92	0.95	0.95	0.96
PM	0.20	0.72	0.76	0.78	0.83	0.90	PM	50	51	51.5	52	52.4	53
(9 Levels)						(12 Levels)							
WD	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.03	WD	1.00	1.00	1.02	1.02	1.03	1.03
FHM	0.42	0.90	1.01	1.01	1.02	1.02	FHM	0.40	0.90	1.01	1.02	1.03	1.03
FSM	0.35	0.80	0.90	0.92	0.95	0.96	FSM	0.35	0.80	0.90	0.92	0.95	0.96
THM	0.38	0.78	0.88	0.90	0.92	0.92	THM	0.38	0.80	0.90	0.92	0.93	0.94
PM	0.30	0.70	0.80	0.82	0.85	0.88	PM	0.33	0.74	0.85	0.87	0.87	0.89

Fig. 11. DVFS results at 60 fps, focusing on normalized energy consumption per frame rate.

By examining the available literature and contrasting with older games, it becomes evident that contemporary games are driven by the quest for enhanced realism, achieved by incorporating more intricate geometry. This shift in paradigm has resulted in a significant rise in the demand on vertex processing. Hence, we introduced low-power optimizations directed at these components. Our implementation demonstrated a substantial 65% improvement in quality, as indicated by a reduction in deadline misses compared to alternative history-based DVFS schemes. Moreover, it resulted in noteworthy energy conservation of 60%. In conclusion, it is clearly understood that graphics applications display workload variations and as a result, low-power optimization techniques have been introduced specifically designed for shader components. Future work includes the use of machine learning algorithms for predicting power consumption in shaders. By training models on historical data and runtime parameters, it may be possible to create more accurate predictions and guide dynamic optimizations.

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Enhancing Road Holding and Vehicle Comfort for an Active Suspension System utilizing Model Predictive Control and Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

Active Suspension Systems (ASS) with control are gaining traction as researchers strive for optimal system performance. They are significant in diverse commercial vehicle applications, catering to user demands. This study employs the advanced Model Predictive Control (MPC) technique to enhance the smoothness and safety of a half-car model. The simulation results showed the prowess of MPC controllers under varied control force signal constraints, demonstrating superiority in curtailing vehicle chassis rotation angle and speed by up to 46.93% and 43.34%, respectively. The controller was compared with an artificial neural network controller utilizing only two state signals of the system, trained from MPC data, demonstrating high accuracy with R^2 reaching 0.97024 and mean squared error at 7.3557×10^{-5} . This study contributes to the refinement of ASS by focusing on practical implementation and performance enhancement.

Keywords-active suspension system; model predictive control; machine learning; deep learning; artificial neural networks; ride comfort; road holding

I. INTRODUCTION

Active Suspension Systems (ASSs) enhance ride comfort, handling, and vehicle stability by dynamically adjusting components, counteracting chassis roll, and optimizing tire contact with the road. ASSs in vehicles use advanced control strategies such as Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID), Fuzzy Logic Network (FLC), and Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) controllers to enhance system criteria. A PID controller uses error feedback to adjust damping forces and maintain the desired suspension response [1]. FLC can use linguistic variables to handle uncertainties and variations in road conditions [2], ensuring smoother ride adaptability. LQR controllers optimize a quadratic cost function to balance ride comfort and stability [3]. These control techniques enable an ASS to continuously adapt and respond to changing road conditions, ensuring optimal performance and safety while providing passengers with a comfortable and controlled ride experience. However, conventional controllers have limited adaptability, struggle with complex systems, and require manual tuning, whereas Model Predictive Control (MPC) offers advanced control capabilities and robustness for complex multivariable systems. This technique is highly effective, seamlessly accommodates system nonlinearities, and excels in diverse applications across industries due to its ability to handle MIMO formulations, various physical restrictions, and multiple objectives [4]. Several studies investigated active suspension system control strategies in automobiles using ISO-based road characteristics [5-7]. According to these simulations, MPC greatly improves suspension performance and power demand

compared to LQR [8-9]. Semi-active vibration control suspension systems use magnetorheological dampers to improve automobile dynamics [10], specifically the quarter vehicle's with semi-active suspension [11-15]. In [16], constrained MPC formulation for longitudinal control and a nonlinear MPC reduced computing cost. In [17], a Particle Swarm-Optimization Model Predictive Controller (PSO-MPC) was used to determine the best control actions. In [14], an explicit MPC approach was presented to supervise the damping force in semi-active vehicle suspensions, and an AFC-based scheme was proposed to control active seat suspension in heavy-duty vehicles. In [18], Parallel Quadratic Programming (PQR), an iterative multiplication technique, was used to address quadratic programming issues in a real-time MPC model. In [19], the focus was on generalization, active suspension test benches, and stability and robustness conditions.

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a powerful and adaptive approach that can be applied effectively to improve the performance of ASSs in vehicles by learning from real-time sensor data and intelligently adjusting suspension components. It effectively models complex relationships and improves ride comfort, stability, and safety, reducing body roll, pitch, and squat during maneuvers [20]. The multifaceted PSO approach has been applied on quarter-car thorax and pelvis models, demonstrating zero head acceleration, low sprung mass acceleration, and equivalent road-holding qualities. In [21-22], ANN models were constructed to accurately predict road holding and ride comfort characteristics. Novel methods have

been proposed for the development of automobile chassis systems that approximate the correlations between design factors and performance indices. In [23], the minimal sensitivity approach was used to generate Pareto-optimal alternatives and evaluate their robustness. Several simulations showed that the B-spline neural network trajectory tracking control architecture is capable of active disturbance suppression [24-25], indicating that ANN, FLC, LQR, and PID controllers are all capable of active disturbance suppression. In [26], an intelligent control strategy for active truck suspensions based on ANNs was presented, with the control arm of the Macpherson suspension system being critical for a comfortable, stable, and safe ride. In [27], a low-cost semi-active car suspension system was presented, with a hydraulic piston and throttle valve replacing passive conventional suspension. In [28], an ANN control technique was used for continuous damping control dampers in car suspension systems to decrease the positional oscillation in road imperfections. In [29], PSO was used for parameter optimization, showing an 84% decrease in iteration resources and a 48% improvement in modeling accuracy for hydraulic adjustable dampers.

II. DESIGN CONTROLLERS FOR HALF-CAR MODEL

A. Vehicle Dynamic Modeling

Figure 1 presents a half-car model with 6 degrees of freedom, simplified with the dynamics equations around the equilibrium as follows:

Fig. 1. Half-car model with ASS.

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{X}_c = & -\frac{c_{af}}{m_c} L_f \dot{\theta}_c \cos \theta_c - \frac{c_{af}}{m_c} \dot{X}_c - \frac{c_{af}}{m_c} \dot{X}_{sf} \\ & - \frac{k_{af}}{m_c} L_f \sin \theta_c - \frac{k_{ar}}{m_c} X_c + \frac{k_{ar}}{m_c} X_{sf} + \frac{1}{m_c} f_{af} \\ & + \frac{c_{ar}}{m_c} L_r \dot{\theta}_c \cos \theta_c - \frac{c_{ar}}{m_c} \dot{X}_c + \frac{c_{ar}}{m_c} \dot{X}_{sr} \\ & + \frac{k_{af}}{m_c} L_r \sin \theta_c - \frac{k_{ar}}{m_c} X_c + \frac{k_{ar}}{m_c} X_{sr} + \frac{1}{m_c} f_{ar} \quad (1) \\ \ddot{\theta}_c = & -L_f^2 \frac{c_{af}}{I_c} \dot{\theta}_c \cos \theta_c - L_f \frac{c_{af}}{I_c} \dot{X}_c + \\ & L_f \frac{c_{af}}{I_c} \dot{X}_{sf} - L_f^2 \frac{k_{af}}{I_c} \sin \theta_c + L_f \frac{k_{af}}{I_c} X_{wf} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -L_f \frac{k_{af}}{I_c} X_c + \frac{L_f}{I_c} f_{af} - L_r^2 \frac{c_{ar}}{I_c} \dot{\theta}_c \cos \theta_c \\ & + L_r \frac{c_r}{I_c} \dot{X}_c - L_r \frac{c_{ar}}{I_c} \dot{X}_{wr} - L_r^2 \frac{k_{ar}}{I_c} \sin \theta_c \\ & + L_r \frac{k_{ar}}{I_c} X_{wr} - L_r \frac{k_{ar}}{I_c} X_{wr} + \frac{L_r}{I_c} f_{ar} \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{X}_{sr} = & -\frac{c_{ar}}{m_{sr}} L_r \dot{\theta}_c \cos \theta_c + \frac{c_{ar}}{m_{sr}} \dot{X}_c - \frac{c_{ar}}{m_{sr}} \dot{X}_{sr} \\ & - \frac{k_{ar}}{m_{sr}} L_r \sin \theta_c + \frac{k_{ar}}{m_{sr}} X_c - \frac{k_{ar}}{m_{sr}} X_{sr} - \frac{c_{pr}}{m_{sr}} \dot{X}_{sr} \\ & + \frac{c_{pr}}{m_{sr}} \dot{X}_{wr} - \frac{k_{pr}}{m_{sr}} X_{sr} + \frac{k_{pr}}{m_{sr}} X_{wr} - \frac{1}{m_{sr}} f_{ar} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{X}_{sf} = & \frac{c_{af}}{m_{sf}} L_f \dot{\theta}_c \cos \theta_c + \frac{c_{af}}{m_{sf}} \dot{X}_c - \frac{c_{af}}{m_{sf}} \dot{X}_{sf} \\ & + \frac{k_{af}}{m_{sf}} L_f \sin \theta_c + \frac{k_{af}}{m_{sf}} X_c - \frac{k_{af}}{m_{sf}} X_{sf} - \frac{k_{pf}}{m_{sf}} X_{sf} \\ & + \frac{k_f}{m_{sf}} X_{wf} - \frac{c_{pf}}{m_{sf}} \dot{X}_{sf} + \frac{c_{pf}}{m_{sf}} \dot{X}_{wf} - \frac{1}{m_{sf}} f_{af} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{X}_{wf} = & \frac{c_{pf}}{m_{wf}} \dot{X}_{sf} - \frac{c_{pf}}{m_{wf}} \dot{X}_{wf} + \frac{k_{pf}}{m_{wf}} X_{sf} - \frac{k_{pr}}{m_{wf}} X_{wf} \\ & - \frac{k_{wf}}{m_{wf}} X_{wf} + \frac{k_{wf}}{m_{wf}} X_{rf} \quad (5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{X}_{wr} = & \frac{c_{pr}}{m_{wr}} \dot{X}_{sr} - \frac{c_{pr}}{m_{wr}} \dot{X}_{wr} + \frac{k_{pr}}{m_{wr}} X_{sr} - \frac{k_{pr}}{m_{wr}} X_{wr} \\ & - \frac{k_{wr}}{m_{wr}} X_{wr} + \frac{k_{wr}}{m_{wr}} X_{rr} \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

B. Model Predictive Control for Active Suspension System

The MPC algorithm revolves around iteratively solving an optimization problem at every time interval. The primary objective is determining the optimal control inputs that minimize a predefined cost function, ensuring adherence to system dynamics and constraints across a finite prediction horizon. This optimization process can be succinctly represented in the following manner:

1) Objective Function

The proposed model seeks to minimize road hold and comfort criteria for the half-car model. The objective function, also known as the cost function, quantifies system performance based on predicted system states and control inputs. This function defines the goal of the control problem and can be customized to meet specific requirements. The general form of the cost function is:

$$J = \sum [q(x_k, u_k) + r(u_k)] \quad (8)$$

where J is the total cost over the prediction horizon, $q(x_k, u_k)$ is the state cost with a function of the predicted system states x_k and control inputs u_k at time step k , and $r(u_k)$ is the control cost which consists of a function of the control inputs at time step k .

2) System Dynamics

The system dynamics, shown in Figure 2, are described by a discrete-time model predicting state evolution over time based on the current state x_k and control inputs u_k :

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k) \quad (8)$$

where $x_{(k+1)}$ is the predicted state at the next time step ($k+1$), and f is the state transition function that describes how the state evolves based on the current state and control input.

Fig. 2. MPC architecture.

3) Constraints

The constraint is to limit the range of allowed controlled force values to ASS to absorb the external vibration from the road transferred to the vehicle. The constraints are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} g(x_k, u_k) &\leq 0 \\ h(x_k) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $g(x_k, u_k)$ is a vector of inequality constraint functions on the states and control inputs, and $h(x_k)$ is a vector of inequality constraint functions on the states.

4) Optimization Problem

MPC aims to find the optimal control inputs that minimize the cost function subject to the system dynamics and constraints over the prediction horizon. The optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimize } J &= \sum [q(x_k, u_k) + r(u_k)] \\ x_{k+1} &= f(x_k, u_k) \\ \text{subject to } g(x_k, u_k) &\leq 0 \\ h(x_k) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The optimization problem is solved each time step, taking the current state of the system as an initial condition. The first control input from the optimal solution is involved in the system, and the procedure is repeated in the subsequent step, effectively employing the receding horizon control. For these proposed MPC models, the Sequential Quadratic Programming (SQP) optimizer is used to define optimal control inputs. It approximates nonlinear problems with quadratic subproblems, linearizing the cost function and constraints at each step to update control input u_k . The process involves iteratively solving these subproblems, aiming to converge to optimal control inputs that satisfy system dynamics and constraints, ultimately enhancing the MPC's ability to handle nonlinear and constrained optimization tasks.

C. Artificial Neural Network for Active Suspension System

A standard ANN architecture for predicting dampers' acting force includes input layers, interconnected hidden layers, and an output layer, is shown in Figure 3. Input features x_i at a given time encompass relevant information, including past observations from the half-car model with signals θ_c and $\dot{\theta}_c$. These features are split into training, testing, and validation sets

(70-20-10) by trial-and-error, transforming weighted connections and activation functions in hidden layers to make predictions. The outputs of the 10 hidden layers at time t are expressed by:

$$h_t^l = \sigma(W_l h_{t-1}^{l-1} + b_l) \quad (11)$$

Fig. 3. Construction of ANN controller for ASS.

In (11), h_t^l signifies the output of the l^{th} hidden layer at time t , W_l denotes the weight matrix governing the connections, h_{t-1}^{l-1} represents the prior hidden layer's output at time $t-1$, b_l is the bias vector, and σ corresponds to the sigmoid activation function. The ultimate output prediction \hat{y}_{t+1} is obtained by applying the final hidden layer's output to the output layer to observe the acting force F_{af} and F_{ar} at ASS for the half-car:

$$\hat{y}_{t+1} = W_o h_n^t + b_o \quad (12)$$

where W_o stands for the weight matrix associated with the output layer, h_n^t denotes the last hidden layer's output at time t , and b_o represents the bias term.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (13)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (14)$$

where N is the number of samples, y_i is the actual target value of the i^{th} sample, \hat{y}_i is the predicted target value of the i^{th} sample, and \bar{y} is the mean of the target values. The parameters of the neural network, which include weights and biases, are iteratively adjusted through the Bayesian regularization backpropagation algorithm. This process aims to minimize the disparity between the network's predicted value \hat{y}_{t+1} and the actual observed value y_{t+1} . The model refines its weights and biases through 156 successive iterations to enhance its predictive accuracy by the Mean Squared Error (MSE) (13) at 7.3557×10^{-5} and $R^2 = 0.97024$ (14). Their ASS characteristics are shown in Figure 4. Figure 4(c) shows the error histogram of the ANN controller, demonstrating the distribution of errors between predicted and actual values within the model performance context. On the horizontal axis, various ranges are displayed, while the vertical axis indicates the frequency of data points within each error interval. This analysis highlights that the error parameters related to the prediction of the ASS control force fall mostly within the approximately ± 45 N range. This alignment with the prescribed constraints of the mechanism strongly validates the feasibility of the proposed approach.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

To assess and simulate the efficacy of the controllers in the context of the ASS applied to a half-car model, the exogenous

disturbance signals originating from the road profile were assumed to be discretized step functions within the simulated time domain. The computer configuration used in the computation was an Intel® Core™ i7-11700F 64GB RAM, NVIDIA GeForce 3080 RTX that trained ANN in 20 min. This modeling approach allows for the analysis of controller performance under realistic road conditions, as expressed by:

$$X_{rf}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t < 1 \\ 0.1 \cdot e^{t-1} & \text{if } t \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$X_{rr}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t < 1 + \text{delay} \\ 0.1 \cdot e^{t-1-\text{delay}} & \text{if } t \geq 1 + \text{delay} \end{cases}$$

Fig. 4. (a) MSE, (b) linear regression, and (c) error histogram of the ANN model.

Figure 5 shows the simulation results of the suggested models under the influence of step pavement profile excitation, with a rate of 1 s applied to the front suspension, 0.4 s to the rear suspension, and valued at 0.1 m. The MPC model with a control force limit of 2000 N is represented by the red dotted line, while the MPC0 model, constrained to a control force of 1500 N, is depicted by the blue dashed line. The solid black line with star remarks depicts the results achieved through the passive suspension model, while the green solid line denotes the results achieved using the ANN controller.

Fig. 5. Time response of chassis with exogenous disturbance: (a) Displacement of chassis and its velocity due to time simulation, (b) Comparing the chassis rotation and its velocity under different controllers.

Figure 5(a) shows a comparison of the chassis attributes, contrasting the use of the ASS system with MPC and ANN controllers against the passive suspension model. It is evident that by increasing the constraint on the damping control force, the performance of the MPC controller within the ASS model exceeds that of the MPC0 controller. Specifically, the reduction in chassis speed is notable, with a decrease of 46% and 43% for the MPC and MPC0 controllers, respectively, compared to the passive suspension model. Figure 5(b) shows that when employing the ANN controller in the ASS system, a notable reduction of 8.82% was achieved in the angular velocity of the chassis, in stark comparison to the results exhibited by the passive suspension model. Table I details the amplitude reduction in the Root Mean Squared (RMS) values of the signals compared to the passive suspension model.

The control forces employed in the ASS models are showcased, contributing to the refinement of the proposed model's smoothness and traction. In response to stepwise excitation, controllers generate damping control forces to mitigate detrimental vibrations that impact both the vehicle and its occupants. These force magnitudes are strategically determined to fulfill the criteria established for the constraint conditions of the model, guided by the MPC control algorithm.

The MPC0 controller adheres to a control force threshold of 1500 N, while the MPC controller adheres to a limit of 2000 N, as in [30-31]. The passive suspension model entirely depends on traditional dampers lacking actuators, leading to a simulation with a control force of 0 N. Figure 5 shows the RMS error values for the X_c , \dot{X}_c , θ_c and $\dot{\theta}_c$ of the models. These observations reveal that the proposed suite of controllers significantly contributes to advancing the controller's initial objectives: vehicle comfort and road holding. Notably, the RMS signals of the system employing the ANN controller exhibit the most substantial reduction, succeeded by the MPC controller and, ultimately, the MPC0 controller. Therefore, in an ideal scenario, the ANN controller optimally utilizes only two measured sensor inputs, namely θ_c and $\dot{\theta}_c$, harnessing the acquired intelligence from the ASS model. This approach effectively minimizes the sensor system expenses for the ASS system while simultaneously maintaining the predetermined objectives with a high precision level.

Fig. 6. RMS values of $\dot{\theta}_c$, θ_c , X_c , and \dot{X}_c .

TABLE I. RMS REDUCTION OF FRONT/REAR WHEELS AND INTERMEDIATE MASSES (%)

Model	X_{sr}	\dot{X}_{sr}	X_{wr}	\dot{X}_{wr}	X_{sf}	\dot{X}_{sf}	X_{wf}	\dot{X}_{wf}
MPC0	14.24	36.07	12.79	43.17	11.32	46.93	4.86	42.02
MPC	14.38	36.18	12.84	43.34	11.24	45.82	5.4	41.04
ANN	11.05	26.97	3.42	4.17	8.77	6.01	0.54	4.99

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to improve vehicle movement smoothness and safety using MPC controllers for a half-car model. The controllers demonstrated adaptability to different conditions, reducing chassis rotation by 46%. The ANN controller was effective in training the ASS system with limited states, achieving an R^2 of 0.97024 and an MSE of 7.3557×10^{-5} . However, directly measuring idealized states can be challenging, prompting future investigations into state estimation algorithms. The study lays the groundwork for exploring deep learning models with unsupervised algorithms, enhancing MPC models for accuracy in uncertain settings, and conducting real-world experiments with disturbances and uncertainties.

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Weber's Law-based Regularization for Blind Image Deblurring

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ABSTRACT

Blind image deblurring aims to recover an output latent image and a blur kernel from a given blurred image. Kernel estimation is a significant step in blind image deblurring and requires a regularization technique to minimize the cost function and the edges of objects to generate a sharp image in a better way. This study proposes a new image regularization technique called Weber's Law Regularization (WLR) based on the Weber law phenomenon. The Weber ratio was used to preserve the edges of small salient objects and to minimize the cost function to obtain a sharp image while minimizing the ringing effect. To validate the WLR, experiments were conducted on benchmark synthetic and real word images and compared with existing state-of-the-art methods. The experimental results showed that WLR can effectively and efficiently deblur images even in the absence of prior knowledge.

Keywords-image deblurring; regularization; Weber's law; Weber's Law Regularization (WLR)

I. INTRODUCTION

Blurring can potentially degrade the quality of an image. In this regard, many techniques have been developed in the field of image processing and computer vision. Motion blur is the most common artifact, which is produced by shaking the camera while capturing an image. Image deblurring is mainly divided into two types: (1) blind image deblurring, where a Point Spread Function (PSF) is not known, and (2) nonblind image deblurring, where a PSF is known. However, the estimation of the PSF or a blur kernel plays a significant role in deblurring the image in both cases. After the estimation of the blur kernel, the sharp image is obtained by using several non-blind deconvolution methods. Blur kernel estimation is further categorized into three types: Variational Bayes (VB)-based methods [1-7], Maximum A Posterior (MAP)-based methods [8-35], and neural network-based frameworks [36-40]. VB methods avoid trivial solutions and are considered to be more

robust theoretically. However, since VB-based approaches are computationally expensive, more efficient methods are required for approximation [5]. Naive MAP-based methods may produce trivial solutions. Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) are used to recover sharp images from blurry images without predicting the blur kernel [36-38]. These methods cannot properly eliminate blur without using the blur kernel and model [39]. Due to certain properties of MAP, VB, and CNN-based methods, this study only considered the first type of deblurring methods.

Salient structures have been used to estimate kernels [8,16, 18-19, 21, 23-25, 41-43]. In [8], two types of filters were used to extract the edges of the salient image, a bilateral filter and a shock filter. In [18-19], an extension of filters was proposed by refining the edges while using data-driven priors. In [21], the informative structures of the edges were selected, while the tiny edges were removed using the relative total variation. In [24],

high-level scene-specific priors were detected for the edges of an image. In [16], a Generalized Shrinkage-Thresholding (GST) operator was used to solve the problem of minimizing the l_p -norm. In [40], a deep generative network regularization was proposed for blind image deconvolution. Sparse regularizations on image gradients have been successfully applied for kernel estimation [2, 9-13, 15, 26-29, 44]. In [26], the l_1 -norm was used to detect the salient edges of objects in a gradient image. The methods proposed in [12-13, 17, 26, 30] produce effective results under certain prior conditions. In [31], the hyper-Laplacian distribution was used to model the image gradients, while the l_p -norm was used as a regularization term. In [9], the quality of an image was improved by combining the l_1 -norm and a ring-suppressing term. In [11], the l_1/l_2 -norm regularization suppressed small and redundant structures, while reweighted norms were also used in [15]. In [10], a new approximation of the l_0 -norm regularizer based on gradients was proposed. In [18], the normalized color-line prior was used to enhance the edge contrast. In [6], a method was proposed to remove the uniform blur shake of the camera from images. Camera shake blur was estimated from image regions without saturation effects selected by users. However, saturated regions of the recovered image had strong artifacts and ringing artifacts near regions of significant object motion. In [7], a fast motion deblurring method was proposed by introducing a prediction step, using image derivatives instead of original pixel values to accelerate the kernel estimation and the latent image. However, the proposed method may not find the global optimal solution if the image has a strong impact on local regions different from other local regions. In [11], a novel type of image regularization for blind deconvolution based on the normalized sparsity measure was proposed. The ratio of l_1 to l_2 norm was proposed for the high-frequency components of an image. The normalized sparsity measure reduced the cost of sharp images. However, this may not work well for objects with sharp edges in an image, because the l_1 to l_2 cannot possess this property.

In [5], a simple modification of the MAP algorithm was proposed, considering the covariance near the latent image with the central pixel x itself. The main drawback of this approach was that it used the standard expectation minimization framework. In [10], an effective method with a generalized l_0 -norm regularizer on gradients was proposed, eliminating the need for extra filtering and reducing the number of iterations required for convergence. However, a moderate ringing effect was still present in the recovered images. In [19], before restoring sharp edges, an external dataset was used to learn the patch and estimate the blur kernel. However, this method may be ineffective when there is a difference between the selected patch and the external dataset. In [18], the contrast was increased to obtain sharp edges utilizing the normalized color line prior. Salient structures were predicted by sharp intermediate patches and further used to estimate the blur kernel. However, this method may not be suitable if the patches have more than two primary colors. In [32], l_0 -regularized priors were used for kernel estimation and to avoid complex filter or explicit edge selection methods. In addition, an alternative minimization method was used to estimate the kernel for convergence in a suitable time. Simplified total variation was used for nonblind deblurring. However, any

better nonblind image deblurring method can be used to improve the results. Dark channel priors capture the changes caused by the blurring process and favor clear over blurred images in the deblurring process [44]. However, this can be less effective in the case of clear images that do not have dark pixels. In [45], extreme channel priors, named Bright Channel Priors (BCPs), were considered because the bright parts of clear images will not remain intact after applying the blurring process. The proposed method also used the benefits of bright- and dark-channel image priors. In addition, in [46] the effect of outliers was minimized when estimating the blur kernel, but at the expense of an increased computational cost. In [47], Probability Weighted Moments Regularization (PWMR) was proposed to better estimate the kernel, using probability-weighted moments in the x and y directions. However, probability weight moments can only perform well for small sample sizes. In [48], a Local Maximum Gradient (LMG) prior was proposed, since the maximum value of the gradient in the local patch will be diminished after the blurring process. Additionally, the proposed method exploited the l_1 -norm. However, this method was computationally inefficient and did not perform well in the presence of Gaussian noise. In [49], a graph-based technique was proposed for blind image deblurring of a single-image photograph, using the Reweighted Graph Total Variation (RGTV) prior as the weight function. This method was unable to handle the defocus blur when not considering the separation of image parts. In [23], a new learning iterative method for blind deconvolution was proposed, using an extended version of the GST operator to minimize l_p -norms that have negative values of p . A GST parameter was defined iteratively to dynamically select the salient edges and time-varying regularization. GST iteratively sharpens the image, ignoring its local details. In [50], the ratio of the Dark Channel Prior (DCP) to the Brilliant Channel Prior (BCP) was considered. In particular, the two-channel priors were obtained from RGB images and used to create an original sparse channel prior first, and then the learned prior was applied to the BID.

Weber's Law (WL) aims to obtain the size of a small difference having a constant proportion to the actual stimulus, i.e. the value of change. In addition, the image affected by camera shake has a small difference between the original and affected pixel values. Moreover, it is difficult to find such a small difference between the affected and original pixels. This study proposes a novel image regularization method, named Weber's Law Regularization (WLR), for blind image deblurring. According to WL, there is a constant difference between the increment threshold and the background intensity. This property was used to estimate the kernel and obtain the sharp image efficiently and effectively. The main contributions of this study are:

- A novel regularization method is proposed based on the WL phenomenon to minimize a cost function to obtain the sharp image.
- The WLR effectively preserves the small texture of an image that was neglected in previous approaches.
- WLR reduces computational cost.

II. BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

WL is extensively used in various image processing and computer vision applications such as to compute image feature descriptors [51], identify impulse noise [52], etc. According to E. Weber, "the size of just noticeable difference is a constant proportion of the original value" [52]. Mathematically, WL is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta I}{I} = K \quad (1)$$

where I is the original value, ΔI is the noticeable Difference Threshold (DT), and $\Delta I/I$ is Weber's fraction. DT is considered the lowest quantity to change stimulus intensity and vary the sensory experience. Moreover, K specifies that Weber's fraction remains stable irrespective of variations in I . By rearranging (1), $\Delta I = IK$ is obtained, which signifies the linear relationship of the incremental threshold and the background intensity in WL.

III. WEBER'S LAW REGULARIZATION (WLR)

To estimate the blur kernel, most techniques neglected the small textures of an image that over-smoothened it. However, ignoring small textures may also eliminate the salient regions of an image. WL provides the relationship between the central pixel and the pixels in a compact neighborhood. In this study, the value of each pixel in the sliding window was calculated. Let x_c be the central pixel in the sliding window, and two filters f_c and f_n , as defined in [52], for the central and neighboring pixels in the sliding window, respectively. Additionally, the central pixel, x_c represents the fraction of two filters obtained by convolving the f_c and f_n with the current sliding window S_w . After convolving the f_c and f_n with S_w , p_c and p_n are obtained, respectively. Equation (2) computes the differences between the central and neighboring pixels within the sliding window S_w by convolving the filter f_n with S_w .

$$p_n = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta x = \sum_{i=1}^n (S_{wi} - x_c), \quad (2)$$

where:

$$S_w = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 & x_1 & x_2 \\ x_3 & x_c & x_4 \\ x_5 & x_6 & x_7 \end{bmatrix}, \quad f_n = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -8 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\text{and } f_c = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

where n is the total number of neighbors in the sliding window, and S_{wi} ($i=1, 2, \dots, n$) denotes the i^{th} neighbor of x_c . Then, p_n and p_c are combined to compute the ratio of differences to the intensity of the central pixel in the sliding window. Therefore, the WLR value of the current sliding window (central pixel) is given by:

$$WLR = \arctan \left[\frac{p_n + \varepsilon}{p_c + \gamma} \right] \quad (3)$$

where ε controls the difference between neighbors and γ is added to not allow the value of the central pixel to be zero. However, the value of WLR may abruptly increase or decrease as the input becomes larger or smaller. Therefore, the arctan function is used to control the value of WLR from being too

large or too small due to its simplicity. Other functions may be used instead of the arctan function. As the fraction p_n/p_c can give some negative values, the logarithm function cannot be used. Discriminative information can be effectively preserved if pixel intensities in the neighborhood are less than the central pixel.

$$WLR = \begin{cases} < 0, & \text{if } x_c > S_{wi} \\ > 0, & \text{if } x_c < S_{wi} \end{cases}$$

Otherwise, the central pixel in the sliding window is lighter than the neighboring pixels.

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

Blind image deblurring models can be described as:

$$v = ku + N \quad (4)$$

where v is the blurred image, k is the unknown blurring matrix, u is the sharp image, and N is the Gaussian noise, which is i.i.d. The main purpose is to blindly estimate the blur matrix k , which will be used to deblur the image. The complete proposed algorithm for image de-blurring is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1

```

Input: Blurred image  $v$ , Maximum kernel size  $k_{max}$ 
Output: Estimated Kernel  $k$ , deblurred image  $u$ 
1. Apply derivative filter to blurry input image  $v$ 
   and get a high-frequency image  $a$ 
2. Blind Estimation of blur matrix  $k$ . Update the
   sharp high-frequency image by using (6)
   Update the blurry matrix  $k$ 
   Continue this step until the fine level is
   obtained
3. Use matrix  $k$  to deblur  $v$  and get the sharp image
 $u$ 

```

A. Blind Kernel Estimation

Kernel estimation plays a significant role in image deblurring. The estimation of the kernel in high frequency provides a better estimation compared to the estimation in the normal image [11]. The high frequencies of noisy and blurred images are used as a prior for kernel estimation. The high frequencies of the noisy and blurry image are obtained by (5). The following filters are used to obtain the high-frequency image:

$$\nabla_x = [1, -1]; \quad \nabla_y = [1, -1]^T \quad (5)$$

After convolving the aforementioned filter with blurry input image v , the following is obtained:

$$a = [\nabla_{xv}, \nabla_{yv}]$$

For spatially invariant blurring, the cost function can be modeled as:

$$WLR = \arctan \left[\frac{p_n + \varepsilon}{p_c + \gamma} \right]$$

$$\min_{x,k} \lambda \|x \otimes k - a\|_2^2 + W + \beta \|k\|_1 \quad (6)$$

where k is the unknown blurring kernel with the constraint that $k \geq 0$ and $\sum ki = 1$, x is the unknown sharp image in the frequency domain, \otimes is a 2D convolution operator, and W is

the proposed regularization term based on the WL phenomenon:

$$W = \sum \frac{WLR_x}{WLR_y} \tag{7}$$

where:

$$WLR_x = WLR(\nabla_x) \text{ and } WLR_y = WLR(\nabla_y)$$

The blur is normally caused by the interaction of the horizontal with the vertical axis or can be a motion on one axis. The proposed regularization method based on the WL phenomenon is shown in (7), indicating that the Weber ratio provides a small distance among the pixels in an image. The first term in (6) shows the likelihood relationship among the kernel, the high-frequency image x , and the unknown sharp image. In (6), the second term shows the novel regularization term proposed in WLR. The third term in (6) is added to remove the noise from the kernel. The constant weights λ and β are used to control the strength of the kernel and the regularization terms. The compact relationship between the central and the neighboring pixels within the sliding window is given by WLR_x and WLR_y , which are obtained by applying a derivative filter along the horizontal and vertical directions. To find a better estimation of the blur kernel, the fraction of WLR_x and WLR_y is computed, and then the summation of the fraction term is used as the regularization term.

Equation (6) is highly non-convex. By initializing the initial kernel k and the high-frequency image x , the problem of high non-convexity can be solved by switching between x and k [6]. The cost function in (6) can be divided into two parts for updating x and k :

$$\min_x \lambda \|xK - a\|_2^2 + W \tag{8}$$

where K is the blurring matrix and:

$$\min_k \lambda \|x \otimes k - a\|_2^2 + \beta \|k\|_1 \tag{9}$$

In each iteration, the Iterative Shrinkage-Thresholding Algorithm (ISTA) [53] was used to update the values in the sharp image using the following parameters: To update x , the regularization parameter λ was set to 20, and the threshold value t was taken as 0.001. Moreover, the observed image a and the maximum iterations N , both inner and outer, were taken as 2 each. The following algorithm was used to update x and the ISTA algorithm was also used for the inner iteration.

```

Algorithm 2: updating  $x$ 
For  $l = 1: M$ 
 $\lambda' = \lambda \|x'\|_2$ 
 $x^{i+1} = \text{ISTA}(k, \lambda', x^i, t, N)$ 
The ISTA algorithm is as follows
for  $I = 1: N$ 
 $c = a - tk^T(x^i - a)$ 
 $x^{i+1} = S_{t\lambda}(c)$ 
end for  $N$ 
end for  $M$ 
Updated image  $x^M$ 
    
```

where S represents the soft shrinkage operation on a vector, and k is the blurring matrix k . ISTA involves the simple multiplication of the blurring matrix k with the sharpening

image x , followed by the shrinkage operation computed component-wise. Each component of the input vector is reduced/shrunked to zero by using the soft shrinkage operator S given by:

$$S_x(x)_i = \max(|x_i| - \alpha, 0) \text{sign}(x_i) \tag{10}$$

After updating x , kernel k is estimated by using the unconstrained Iterative Re-weighted Least Squares (IRLS) method [11]. IRLS is just used for one iteration, in which the weights are computed from the previous updated k . At the finest level, the estimated kernel may have a few values that are negligible or so small that they are normalized to 0. These values may appear likely due to noise. Some previous studies also have used similar blind de-convolution techniques [6]. For a multi-scale estimation of the kernel, a coarse-to-fine pyramid of image resolutions was used to overcome the problem of estimating the large kernel.

B. Image Deblurring

After kernel estimation, different nonblind deconvolution methods can be used to recover the sharp image at the finest level [10, 23, 30]. Richardson-Lucy (RL) is the most used method for non-blind image deconvolution. However, if the estimated kernel is not estimated correctly, then RL can produce ringing effect in the deconvolved image. To avoid this problem, fast image deconvolution was used with hyper-laplacian priors after kernel estimation, which is fast and robust against small kernel errors [30].

$$\min_x \lambda \|x \otimes k - y\|_2^2 + \|\nabla_x\|_b + \|\nabla_y\|_b \tag{11}$$

where ∇_x and ∇_y are the same derivative filters used in (5). The above cost function is solved by lp-type regularization. The values of λ and b were 3000 and 0.8, respectively, as in [11].

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Real-world and synthetic images were used to compare the performance of the proposed WLR method and state-of-the-art deblurring methods, such as those in [2, 5-6, 8, 10-11, 13, 19, 20-21, 23, 25, 27, 44, 47, 54]. Two quantitative measures were used to evaluate performance.

A. Synthetic Data

A standard benchmark dataset [12] was used to validate the effectiveness of the proposed method. This dataset consists of four 255x255 images and eight different blur kernels with sizes varying from 13x13 to 27x27. After convolution, there were 32 images in total. Blurred images, ground-truth images, and ground-truth kernels were also provided. The parameter settings in [11] were followed by using the same nonblind deconvolution algorithm to evaluate the estimated kernels. It was seen that the kernel estimated by WLR produced better results compared to other methods. The experimental results showed that the kernel estimated using WLR effectively preserves the edges of an object compared to various state-of-the-art methods [5-6, 7-14, 18, 21, 44]. Table I shows a detailed comparison of WLR with other methods in terms of PSNR, SSIM, and computational time, showing that the proposed method outperformed the others in terms of optimal error ratios.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT METHODS ON SYNTHETIC IMAGE DATASET [12] USING DIFFERENT PARAMETERS

Method/ Image	PSNR	SSIM	Time (s)	Error ratio
Known k	32.32	0.9385	---	1.0000
[8]	28.87	0.8845	2.3942	1.4082
[10]	29.41	0.9000	2.9371	1.4071
[11]	28.22	0.8586	10.1178	2.1369
[12]	28.73	0.8916	80.5917	1.5531
[14]	30.1332	0.9119	12.7206	1.2198
[19]	30.60	0.9190	192.5495	1.2234
[44]	30.87	0.9203	28.37	1.1934
[47]	30.14	0.9122	25.1276	1.2271
[54]	30.32	0.9034	10.11	1.23
WLR	30.37	0.9123	7.3562	1.2693

B. Real-World Images

Real-world standard benchmark images were also used to evaluate the performance of the proposed WLR regularization method and compare it with [2, 5-6, 8, 21, 10-11, 13-14, 19-20, 23, 25, 27, 44], using the same parameters for all real-world images. The proposed method effectively restored the image edges compared to the other methods, as it provided less ringing effects and better texture preservation in the zoomed part of the image. The methods from [2, 6, 11, 14, 21] over-smoothed the image while ignoring the small textures, while the proposed method preserved the small salient regions. WLR was effective in preserving the edges and provided sharper images than the other methods. WLR can capture the compact relationship between the pixels in the sliding window. The methods in [23, 44] over-smoothed the images eliminating small textures. Moreover, they only considered the prominent textures from the image and ignored the local information of the patches. The method in [23] also gave high contrast and a strong ringing effect. WLR reduced the ringing effect and preserved the underlying edge details. This is most likely because WLR incorporates even the smallest information of the objects. The image recovered by the method in [25] has a strong blurring effect. The image recovered by the method in [13] had an increased contrast and was brighter. The method proposed in [11] uses the fraction l_1/l_2 as a regularization term. The difference of each point from all other points was computed with this type of fraction and resulted in an increased computational cost. Furthermore, the relationship in the local sliding window was not considered.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a new regularization method based on Weber's law for blind image deconvolution. The Weber law tends to minimize the cost function. In addition, the proposed regularization method produced sharp images effectively and efficiently. To validate the effectiveness of WLR, experiments were conducted on both synthetic and real-world images. The experimental results showed the effectiveness of the WLR compared to other state-of-the-art blind image deblurring methods. WLR was found to be efficient and effective for the analysis of real-world images even though sometimes it did not perform that well for synthetic images. In the future, the WLR may be incorporated with a neural network to estimate the kernel.

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A Laser Cutting Machine Prototype

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, laser cutting technology stands as one of the most cutting-edge technologies. Not only do laser cutting machines play a crucial role in the mechanical engineering industry, but also in numerous other industries including electronic circuit manufacturing, garment manufacturing, and particularly in the handicraft industry. This study presents a methodology for the design and production of laser cutting machines in Vietnam. A laser cutting machine has been successfully constructed, featuring a straightforward configuration, user-friendly operation, and low cost. The machine has the ability to perform laser cutting on wooden materials, achieving a cutting depth ranging from 1 to 2 mm. The proposed laser cutting machine prototype can cut at a speed of 1000 mm/min, thus meeting the specified requirements.

Keywords-laser cutting; prototype; machine; design

I. INTRODUCTION

Laser cutting machines have played a crucial role in solving the critical need for automating the production process, leading to significant advancements in reliability and quality [1-5]. From a scientific standpoint, these machines have effectively addressed the challenge of cutting and engraving intricate shapes on various materials of any dimension within the manufacturing industry. Alongside with the conventional cutting methods, such as milling and turning [6-8], laser cutting technology finds application in the industries of electronics, medicine, aerospace, and automobile. A common use of this technology involves the cutting of various metals, including tungsten, aluminium, steel, brass, and nickel [9-12]. Lasers are preferred for their ability to deliver precise cuts and achieve impeccable surface finishes. In addition, lasers are employed to cut ceramic, silicon, and other metallic films [13-17]. Laser cutting machines in Vietnam have enhanced the automation capabilities of companies by reducing the number of operators required and minimizing the need for manual intervention in machine operations, subsequently leading to a decrease of operational errors. Nevertheless, in Vietnam, the research, manufacturing, and implementation of laser cutting in production faces many limitations. The majority of laser

cutting machines are currently utilized by companies that specialize in processing and manufacturing molds on a large scale. Moreover, those machines currently available in the market are prohibitively expensive and do not fit with the income conditions of most Vietnamese individuals. Laser cutting machines are infrequently utilized in small manufacturing workshops and university laboratories. In order to address the existing challenges, many industries and certain universities have been actively endeavouring to produce laser cutting machines which will meet both manufacturing and research demands. This article presents a plan for developing and implementing an inexpensive prototype laser cutting machine that fulfils essential operational requirements for manufacturing and business purposes.

II. LASER CUTTING TECHNOLOGY

Laser cutting involves the utilization of a projector to concentrate laser beams into a singular focus point. The concentrated focus point possesses immense energy capable of incinerating the surface or target requiring laser impact. The device emits a significant amount of thermal energy across a wide range of wavelengths, enabling it to etch various materials including metal, wood, leather, fabric, and others. Laser cutting machines exhibit superior performance in comparison to CNC

machines on a wide range of materials including metals, alloys, and non-metals like glass, plastic, and mica with greater ease. Furthermore, laser cutting technology is characterized by its minimal noise emissions and negligible impact on workers. Laser cutting machines function by utilizing a laser beam as a focused and intense heat source. Subsequently, you can effortlessly sever materials of varying hardness and thickness, including metals like stainless steel, copper, iron, steel, and aluminium, as well as non-metallic materials.

III. DESIGN LASER CUTTING MACHINE

A. Working Principle

The laser cutting machine model represents the operational principle of a CNC machine that is controlled by specialized software and applied in practical settings. The laser cutting machine uses a concentrated beam of energy produced by the laser, which is directed onto the surface of the product through the lens system of the machine. Table I provides a comprehensive overview of the primary technical specifications that must be met for the laser cutting machine. The machine has the capability to cut a workpiece with dimensions of 250×250 mm. It operates at a cutting speed of 500 mm/min and can engrave to a depth of less than 2 mm. On average, it takes 60 min to complete a cutting operation. Figure 1 illustrates the initial design of the machine prototype along with its corresponding working principle. First, the control software will convert the loaded image data into G-code for cutting purposes. The motor (1) transfers motion to the assembly (4) that holds the laser diode by means of the lead screw and nut set (3). Consequently, the laser diode's axis (5) will align precisely with the X-coordinate currently indicated on the control software. The motor (2) transfers motion to the machine table (6) via the lead screw and the nut assembly (7). Thus, the laser diode's axis (5) will align with the Y coordinate of the current point indicated on the control software. Once the point coordinates are established, the laser diode (5) releases a laser beam. The beam possesses a significant amount of energy, enabling it to effectively heat the surface of the product at the specific point of focus. This, in turn, facilitates the material melting. The liquefied substance will be displaced from its initial location by a forceful flow of gas that is aligned with the laser beam. The molten region will persistently undergo elongation along the trajectory of the laser beam, resulting in a cleave and the formation of the desired shape.

Fig. 1. The laser cutting machine model was designed using NX 12.

TABLE I. MACHINE'S TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Machine specification	Value
Cutting speed	500 mm/min
Depth of cut	≤ 2 mm
Cutting time	≤ 60 min
Workpiece size	250x250 mm

B. Calculating the Motor Requirements

The motor controls the movement of the laser beam along both the X and Y axes. Motors that operate in both the X and Y directions typically have equal power. The weight of the moving parts encompasses the structure of the X and Y axis assemblies.

1) Y Axis Motor

- Sliding friction coefficient: $\mu = 0.12$.
- Lead screws with steps: $P_b = 8$ mm.
- The mass of the moving part is the machine table: $M_y = 1$ kg.
- Mechanical advance: $\eta = 0.9$.
- Angle of axle inclination: $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $i = 0.9$.
- Friction force: $F_m = 0.7$ N.
- The frictional moment M_{fric} is calculated as:

$$M_{fric} = \frac{m \cdot g \cdot \mu \cdot h \cdot \cos \alpha}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot i \cdot \eta} = 0.0012 \text{ Nm} \quad (1)$$

- The appropriate 8 mm lead screw diameter is chosen for the given speed:

$$v_{max} = \frac{\pi \cdot D \cdot n}{60 \cdot 1000} = 0.84 \text{ m/s} \quad (2)$$

- The moment of resistance caused by the static friction of the moving component M_{mach} is calculated by:

$$M_{mach} = \frac{\mu \cdot F_b}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot i \cdot \eta \cdot v_{max}} = 0.093 \text{ N.m} \quad (3)$$

- The actuator is positioned in a horizontal orientation and then $\alpha = 0^\circ \rightarrow M_{wy} = 0$.
- The moment required to operate the Y axis is denoted as M_{start} and is calculated by:

$$M_{start} = M_{fric} + M_{wy} + M_{mach} = 0.0942 \text{ Nm} \quad (4)$$

2) Select X Axis Motor

- Sliding friction coefficient: $\mu = 0.12$.
- Lead screws with steps: $P_b = 8$ mm.
- The mass of the moving part is the machine table: $m = W_y = 0.8$ kg.
- Mechanical advance: $\eta = 0.9$.
- Angle of axle inclination: $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $i = 0.9$.
- Friction force: $F_m = 0.7$ N.
- Frictional moment:

$$M_{fric} = \frac{mg\mu.h.\cos\alpha}{2\pi.i.\eta} = 0.0009 \text{ N.m} \quad (5)$$

- The appropriate 8 mm lead screw diameter is chosen for the given speed.

$$v_{max} = \frac{\pi.D.n}{60.1000} = 0.84 \text{ m/s} \quad (6)$$

- Moment of resistance caused by the static friction of the moving component

$$M_{mach} = \frac{\mu.F_b}{2\pi.i.\eta.v_{max}} = 0.093 \text{ N.m} \quad (7)$$

- The actuator is positioned in a horizontal orientation and then $\alpha = 0^\circ \rightarrow M_{wx} = 0$.

- Moment required to operate the X axis:

$$M_{start} = M_{fric} + M_{wx} + M_{mach} = 0.09396 \text{ Nm} \quad (8)$$

According to the parameters calculated from (4) and (8), the NEMA 17 stepper motor is chosen for the machine prototype.

C. Mechanical Design for Laser Cutting Machine

Figure 2 shows the components of a mechanical structure. The machine indicates a simple structure comprising 23 main parts. Following the thorough design process, each intricate detail is manufactured in accordance with specific standards, including hexagonal screws, nuts, screws, and aluminium bars. We were based on preexisting frameworks to reduce costs.

Fig. 2. Main parts of laser cutting machine. (1) Laser hoder, (2) shaft $\phi 80 \times 80$ mm, (3) LMK10UU, (4) lead screw $\phi 8 \times 400$ mm, (5) shaft $\phi 10 \times 400$ mm, (6) X-axis holder, (7) Nema step motor, (8) aluminum bar $20 \times 20 \times 330$ mm, (9) L corner, (10) motor holder, (11) aluminum bar $20 \times 20 \times 330$ mm (11), (12) table, (13) LM10UU, (14) shaft $\phi 10 \times 330$ mm, (16) Y-axis holder, (17) aluminum bar $20 \times 20 \times 360$, (18) diode laser, (19) diode laser holder, (20) X-axis holder, (21) coupling, (22) Y-axis holder, (23) lead screw $\phi 8 \times 80$ mm.

1) Machine Frame

The machine table base is constructed using 20×20 mm extruded aluminum bars. It has a mass of approximately 4 kg, with a total size of $400 \times 330 \times 220$ mm (length, width, and height), as depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Machine frame overall dimensions.

Fig. 4. Stress simulation.

Fig. 5. Deformation.

The combined mass of the machine table and other assemblies is 2 kg. To meet the frame detail requirement, it is sufficient to load the frame detail and other supporting details, resulting in a total mass of $m = 6$ kg. Figure 4 illustrates the results of the stress test performed on the machine frame. The minimum stress measured is 0.022 MPa, while the maximum stress reached is 0.264 MPa. The machine ensures strength by working within the allowable stress limit (yield strength) of 229 MPa. Figure 5 shows the process of evaluating the frame deformation, with the maximum deformation measuring 2.273×10^{-3} mm. Therefore, the frame design fully satisfies the design requirements. Figure 6 illustrates the structural framework of the machine in its complete state.

Fig. 6. A machine frame prototype.

2) Machine Table and Other Parts

Once the machine frame has been fabricated, the remaining components of the machine are produced using the 3D printing technique. PLA printing plastic is utilized, with a printing temperature of 205 °C and a printing layer thickness of 0.2 mm. Components such as fasteners and shafts are pre-purchased. Figure 7 displays the prototype of the laser cutting machine.

Fig. 7. A prototype of the laser cutting machine.

Fig. 8. The graphic screen of the LaserGRBL software.

3) Machine Control System

In order to perform the laser cutting procedure, one must control the speed and power of the laser diode by using LaserGRBL software, which is widely recognized and performed on mini-CNC machines [18-20]. Figure 8 displays the software interface. The central circuit controls the laser power circuits and receives feedback signals from the sensor through software used on the computer. With 24 V, input power is supplied to the A4988 driver to control the motors on the machine's axes and 12 V is supplied to the driver to control the laser. Signals output from the control center. The electrical connection can be seen in [21]. The block diagram of control algorithm is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 9. Block diagram of the control algorithm.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The machine functions with stability and precision, successfully cutting according to the intended specifications and accomplishing multiple predetermined objectives. Figure 10 shows the prototype machine during the working process. Table II presents a summary of the technical specifications of the laser cutting machine prototype. The machine has a cutting speed of 1000 mm/min, a cutting depth ranging from 1 to 2 mm, and a maximum workpiece size of 312×260 mm.

Figure 11 depicts several products made from wood and plastic cut by the machine prototype. The machine demonstrates good cutting precision of around ± 0.2 mm, thus fully meeting the specified requirements. Due to its low manufacturing cost, the suggested machine is highly suitable for developing countries such as Vietnam considering their typical economy state.

Fig. 10. Operating machine.

Fig. 11. Products from the laser cutting machine.

TABLE II. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF MACHINE PROTOTYPE

Machine specification	Value
Cutting speed	1000 mm/min
Quality cutting	5 lines/mm
Depth of cut	1-2 mm
Workpiece size	312×260 mm

V. CONCLUSION

The article presents a systematic approach for developing and producing a prototype of a laser cutting machine, encompassing stages such as calculation, design, simulation, and manufacturing. The experimental results demonstrate that the machine effectively fulfills fundamental functionalities. The machine has a diminutive dimension of 400×330×250 mm and is capable of severing workpieces measuring 300×250 mm with a maximum cutting profundity of 2 mm. The machine is produced at a relatively inexpensive price in comparison to comparable products.

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Integral Backstepping Sliding Mode Control for Maximizing the Power Production of Wind Turbines

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ABSTRACT

Wind turbine control has attracted increasing attention, driven in part by evolving challenges due to the growing size and complexity of wind turbines. Addressing these challenges and maximizing wind turbine power production requires the application of advanced nonlinear control methods. Sliding Mode Control (SMC) has emerged as a promising approach in this context. Recent studies have explored the integration of an integral term with SMC, called I-SMC. This technique has been shown to result in system responses that exhibit chattering phenomena with noticeable state errors. This study aimed to address these issues through the introduction of a novel controller known as Integral Backstepping SMC (IB-SMC). This study demonstrated that IBSMC not only ensured the stability of wind turbines but also outperformed other control strategies, even in the presence of disturbances of approximately 30% of the rated electromagnetic torque. To validate the effectiveness of the proposed controller, extensive simulation tests were carried out using MATLAB /Simulink software to evaluate the controller's responsiveness to rapid changes in conditions, as well as its robustness and overall performance. A comparison was carried out between the IBSMC and previous SMCs to evaluate their ability to reduce steady-state error and chattering.

Keywords-wind turbines; stability; integral sliding mode control; backstepping control; nonlinear systems

I. INTRODUCTION

The last few years have seen an increase in interest in the control of wind turbines, partially motivated by the increasing complexity associated with the management of such large devices [1-4]. The bigger the turbines, the more challenges researchers face in designing their control. To complicate this scenario even further, researchers must consider which control

works best when the wind turbine operates at variable or fixed rotor speed. When in operation, wind turbines can move between two distinct modes, called partial load and full load. For the partial-load case, the control objective is to maintain a steady tip-speed ratio and use this information to extract the maximum possible energy by tracking the wind and the turbine shaft speeds. However, in the full-load case, the control objective is to maintain the generator speed at its rated value

independently of the wind speed [1, 3, 5]. The control of wind turbines comprises two clear goals:

- Maximizing power production when the turbine operates at its normal speed
- Regulating power production at a specific level when the wind speed exceeds a certain threshold.

A wide range of control methods have been proposed to maximize power production, including linear, nonlinear, and data-driven control [1, 3, 6-8]. Although linear control methods have shown promising results [9], many studies have shown that nonlinear control for wind turbines outperforms linear control [2-3, 7]. Sliding Mode Control (SMC) has attracted attention and has been widely used to control nonlinear processes subjected to external disturbances [10-13]. A switching function, known as the sliding manifold, is selected to drive the system trajectories to reach the manifold (i.e. the sliding surface). This means that all system trajectories will reach the sliding surface and will remain there forever [11, 13].

In terms of wind turbines, SMC has proved its effectiveness in wind turbine control. In [5], promising results were achieved when using SMC based on the Utkin method and considering a two-mass drive train model with integral action to minimize errors. In [14], the Utkin method was applied in the setup of a single mass model with fuzzy representation. In [15], the importance of SMC for wind turbines was presented, showing improvements when SMC works with a time-varying compensator to compute the sliding surface. I-SMC has gained popularity because the integral term ensures that the system error goes to zero as the system evolves. As with SMC, I-SMC relies upon a sliding surface that drives the system state to a desired equilibrium point and the additional integral term helps to eliminate the steady-state error. I-SMC improves the performance of wind turbines in the presence of disturbances [16]. In [17], I-SMC was proposed when extracting maximum power at below-rated wind speed [17]. In [18], I-SMC was investigated to improve the performance of permanent magnet synchronous wind turbine generators [18]. Backstepping [19] is a nonlinear control strategy that, combined with SMC, can significantly improve the process response, for example, in photovoltaics [20], robot manipulators [21], vehicles [22], quadrotors [23], and wind turbines [24-25]. In [24-25], the benefits of backstepping with SMC were presented. However, tracking has not yet been fully solved under backstepping with SMC. Tracking requires an integral term, recall, to drive the system to the desired tracking point. In [24-25] backstepping was used with SMC (B-SMC) in the context of wind turbines, but B-SMC does not ensure tracking. However, IB-SMC ensures tracking. IB-SMC has already been investigated in other contexts, such as DFIG [6, 26], quadrotors [27] magnetic levitation [28], optoelectronic platforms [29], and photovoltaic energy [30]. This study contributes toward this direction by presenting a strategy that joins the integral term with both backstepping and SMC, contributing the following:

- IB-SMC is proposed for wind turbines to reduce chattering by giving a high nonlinearity on the switching manifold using inner loops.

- The chattering problem of SMC due to the linearity of the sliding surface is addressed.
- An integral term is considered to improve the precision of the system, as concluded from I-SMC.
- The robustness and closed-loop stability of the proposed control law is tested.
- The controller's parameters are optimized to meet the required objectives in terms of stability, precision, and chattering mitigation.

II. MODELING

Wind turbines depend on certain mechanical and electric elements to produce electricity. The aerodynamic power extracted from the turbine's shaft is given by [3, 8, 31]:

$$P_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi C_p(\lambda, \beta) v^3 R^2 \quad (1)$$

where R , v , and ρ denote the rotor radius, wind speed, and air density (kg/m^3), respectively. C_p is the turbine's aerodynamic efficiency that is highly dependent on the tip speed ratio (λ) and the blade pitch angle (β). According to Betz's limit, the power factor $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ never exceeds the value of 0.593 [32]. The tip-speed ratio λ is given by (2) [24, 33]:

$$\lambda = \frac{R\omega_r}{v} \quad (2)$$

where ω_r is the rotational speed of the wind turbine. The power coefficient $C_p(\lambda, \beta)$ required in (1) can be expressed by [34]:

$$C_p(\lambda, \beta) = 0.0068\lambda + 0.5176 \left(\frac{116}{\eta} - 0.4\beta - 5 \right) e^{(-21\eta^{-1})} \quad (3)$$

with η satisfying: $\frac{1}{\eta} = \frac{1}{(\lambda+0.08\beta)} - \frac{0.035}{(\beta^3+1)}$.

Aerodynamic torque is expressed as follows [17, 35-36]:

$$T_a = \frac{1}{2\lambda} \rho \pi R^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) v^2 \quad (4)$$

A. Power Transmission Modeling

The mechanism of a wind turbine contains a drivetrain, which names the group of gears that make the conversion of mechanical energy from the low-speed shaft to the electric generator. The corresponding equations are [39]:

$$J_r \dot{\omega}_r = T_a - T_{ls} - K_r \omega_r \quad (5)$$

$$J_g \dot{\omega}_g = T_{hs} - K_g \omega_g - T_{em} \quad (6)$$

where T_a (T_{ls}) is the aerodynamic (low-speed) shaft torque. Low-speed shaft speed is denoted by ω_{ls} , and rotor side (generator side) angular deviation is denoted by ω_r (ω_g). The high-speed shaft torque T_{hs} propels the generator's inertia J_g while the generator torque T_g and the generator damping K_g act as brakes. Since the low-speed and high-speed shaft torque are related through the rule $T_{ls} = N_g T_{hs}$, (6) can be used to write:

$$T_{ls} = N_g (J_g \dot{\omega}_g + K_g \omega_g + T_{em}) \quad (7)$$

Combining (5) and (7) gives:

$$J_r \dot{\omega}_r = T_a - T_{ls} - K_r \omega_r \quad (8)$$

III. CONTROL SYSTEM

Wind turbines are designed to generate electricity as efficiently as possible. Industrial wind turbines achieve maximum power efficiency when the wind crosses the turbine blades at a speed of 10 to 15 m/s [8]. When the wind speed exceeds 15 m/s, the turbine can be damaged and a safer strategy is to slow down the shaft speed. In this case, all additional power that could be extracted from the wind must be discharged. Industrial wind turbines have a built-in power-regulation mechanism for any kind of wind. When the output power is lower than the rated power, wind turbines must respond to rapid variations. Typically, the turbine operates at variable rotor speeds to capture the maximum available wind energy, and the torque generator provides input control by varying the rotor speed while keeping the blade pitch angle constant. Various control methods have been proposed, some combining linear and nonlinear control techniques or employing more advanced control strategies. Most of these methods involve multiple objectives and some of them aim to control the rotor speed reference.

This study aims to design a control method that maximizes power extraction. This was achieved under the following considerations. Controlling wind turbines usually requires dealing with two inputs and two outputs [14, 40]. In formal terms, the two inputs are the blade pitch angle β_{reg} and the electromagnetic torque of the generator T_{em} . The two outputs are the generated electrical power P and the turbine rotation speed ω_r . Both β and λ in (1) are maintained at their optimal values to achieve the control goal. In particular, to obtain the optimal value for λ , the rotor speed ω_r must follow the optimal reference rotor speed ω_{ropt} . This is achieved by modifying the control input signal T_g .

A. Baseline Control

Baseline control denotes the classical control strategy that regulates the generator torque to maximize power output at varying wind speeds. This control strategy is the most commonly used and studied controller in wind turbines [1-3]. The baseline control works as follows. The turbine sets the blade pitch angle to zero to extract the maximum energy. Afterward, the wind turbine operates under generator torque control T_g through [5, 41]:

$$T_g = \frac{1}{2\lambda_{opt}^3} \rho \pi R^5 C_{pmax} \omega_r^2 \quad (9)$$

B. Sliding Mode Control

Although SMC has been successfully applied in the control of wind turbines, it is known to have a side effect: SMC creates chattering, a phenomenon that makes the system oscillate with increasing frequency [12]. Several attempts have been made to mitigate the impact of chattering. One of them is to apply control with saturation or hyperbolic tangent functions. The control law then ensures that the system remains on the sliding surface, and any abrupt changes in the control are replaced by a smoother variation function, which is then added to the continuous control term. This feature is recalled in the sequence.

There are two significant steps in the SMC design process. The first is to define the switching surface to achieve the required system dynamics. To extract the maximum power at below-rated wind speed (e.g. 15 m/s), the turbine rotor speed must track the reference rotor speed, which is derived from the effective wind speed. The second step is to choose the control law that drives the trajectories to the switching surface. For both steps, the sliding surface can be defined by [24, 35, 42]. The corresponding asymptotic stability is ensured if the Lyapunov function $V = S^2$ satisfies $\dot{V} = S, S < 0$, following:

$$\dot{V} = S \left(\frac{T_a}{J_r} - \frac{K_r}{J_r} \omega_r - \frac{N_g J_g}{J_r} \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{N_g K_g}{J_r} \omega_g - \frac{N_g}{J_r} T_{em} - \dot{\omega}_{ref} \right) \quad (10)$$

where T_{em} represents the control law applied in the wind turbine. The scalar terms u_{equ} and u_{disc} are defined as:

$$u_{equ} = \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \omega_r \pm \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \omega_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref}$$

$$u_{disc} = -K \tanh\left(\frac{S}{\phi}\right), K > 0 \quad (11)$$

where K represents a proportional gain and $\phi > 0$ is a constant related to the region around the desired operating point. The control law applied in the wind turbine is:

$$T_{em} = u = u_{equ} + u_{disc} = \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \omega_r$$

$$- J_g \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \omega_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref} - K \tanh\left(\frac{S}{\phi}\right) \quad (12)$$

C. Integral Sliding Mode Control

Conventional SMC acts to minimize the error between the measured output and the desired operating point [34]. However, this strategy sometimes leads to a slow convergence to the desired operating point, especially if the system has a steady-state error. I-SMC incorporates an integral term to minimize the tracking error [2, 35]. Formally, the I-SMC reads as [31, 43-44]:

$$S(t) = e(t) + K_i \int_0^\infty e(t) dt \quad (13)$$

with $e(t) = \omega_r(t) - \omega_{ref}(t)$. Considering the Lyapunov function as $V = S^2$, gives:

$$\dot{V} = S(\dot{e}(t) + K_i e(t)) = S \left(\frac{T_a}{J_r} - \frac{K_r}{J_r} \omega_r - \frac{N_g J_g}{J_r} \dot{\omega}_g \right.$$

$$\left. - \frac{N_g K_g}{J_r} \omega_g - \frac{N_g}{J_r} T_{em} - \dot{\omega}_{ref} + K_i e(t) \right) \quad (14)$$

Then, obtain $\dot{V} < 0$ whenever the control torque T_{em} satisfies:

$$T_{em} = \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \omega_r - J_g \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \omega_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref}$$

$$+ \frac{J_r}{N_g} K_i e(t) - K \tanh\left(\frac{S}{\phi}\right) \quad (15)$$

D. Integral-Backstepping SMC (IB-SMC)

IB-SMC combines I-SMC with backstepping [45-47]. Like the I-SMC, IB-SMC handles and minimizes the error as quickly as possible. Backstepping transforms lower-order systems into a strict feedback form [24, 43, 48]. The integral-backstepping technique can be adapted and merged with SMC to generate a smooth output signal, thereby removing any

chattering in the control input. IB-SMC is an important step in overcoming certain limitations of conventional SMC, such as chattering, steady-state error, and tracking errors resulting from uncertainties and disturbances. Compared to traditional backstepping control, the integration of integral backstepping with SMC improves robustness against external disturbances by avoiding discontinuous control signals and improving tracking accuracy.

The tracking error ε_1 is defined as :

$$\varepsilon_1 = \omega_r - \omega_{ref} \quad (16)$$

As usual, the goal is to ensure that ε_1 tends to zero as t tends to infinity. Taking the derivative to time on both sides of (16), with (8) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\varepsilon}_1 = & \frac{T_a}{J_r} - \frac{K_r}{J_r} \omega_r - \frac{N_g J_g}{J_r} \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{N_g K_g}{J_r} \omega_g - \frac{N_g}{J_r} T_{em} \\ & - \dot{\omega}_{ref} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The candidate Lyapunov function is:

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_1^2 + k \frac{1}{2} \xi^2 \quad (18)$$

where $\xi(t) = \int_0^t (\omega_r - \omega_{ref}) dt$ is the rotor speed error. The first time derivative of (18), is:

$$\dot{V}_1 = \varepsilon_1 \left(\frac{T_a}{J_r} - \frac{K_r}{J_r} \omega_r - \frac{N_g J_g}{J_r} \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{N_g K_g}{J_r} \omega_g - \frac{N_g}{J_r} T_{em} - \dot{\omega}_{ref} + k \xi \right) \quad (19)$$

$K_1 > 0$ is defined as the constant that satisfies $\dot{V}_1 = -K_1 \varepsilon_1^2$, resulting in:

$$\begin{aligned} -K_1 \varepsilon_1 = & \frac{T_a}{J_r} - \frac{K_r}{J_r} \omega_r - \frac{N_g J_g}{J_r} \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{N_g K_g}{J_r} \omega_g - \frac{N_g}{J_r} T_{em} \\ & - \dot{\omega}_{ref} + k \xi \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

The T_{em} variable is considered a virtual control input, meaning that it will drive (17) to the equilibrium zero point. A stabilizing function ς is derived, which is assumed to be identical to the virtual control input T_{em} to lead to the desired stability. The stabilizing function is defined as:

$$\varsigma = \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \omega_r - J_g \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \omega_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref} + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K \xi \quad (21)$$

The second error variable is defined as:

$$\varepsilon_2 = T_{em} - \varsigma \quad (22)$$

Substituting (22) into (17) gives:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_1 = \frac{T_a}{J_r} - \frac{K_r}{J_r} \omega_r - \frac{N_g J_g}{J_r} \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{N_g K_g}{J_r} \omega_g - \dot{\omega}_{ref} - \frac{N_g}{J_r} (\varsigma) \quad (23)$$

Combining (18) and (20) gives:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_1 = -K_1 \varepsilon_1 - K \xi - \frac{N_g}{J_r} \varepsilon_2 \quad (24)$$

As a result, using (15) gives:

$$\dot{V}_1 = \varepsilon_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 + K \xi \dot{\xi} = -K_1 \varepsilon_1^2 - \frac{N_g \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2}{J_r} \quad (25)$$

It should be noted that the term $-K_1 \varepsilon_1^2$ is negative. However, the term $N_g \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 / J_r$ can become either positive or negative when $t > 0$ increases. The next argument is introduced

to ensure that $N_g \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2 / J_r$ becomes negative for all $t > 0$, and so ensuring that \dot{V}_1 is negative for all $t > 0$, following (21) and (22):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\varsigma} = & \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_r - J_g \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref} + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K \dot{\xi} \\ & + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\varepsilon}_2 = & \dot{T}_{em} - \frac{T_a}{N_g} + \frac{K_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_r + J_g \dot{\omega}_g + K_g \dot{\omega}_g + \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref} \\ & - \frac{J_r}{N_g} K \dot{\xi} - \frac{J_r}{N_g} K_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

According to Step 2, the Lyapunov function becomes [30]:

$$V_2 = V_1 + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_2^2 \quad (28)$$

which implies:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_2 = & \dot{V}_1 + \varepsilon_2 \dot{\varepsilon}_2 = -K_1 \varepsilon_1^2 - \frac{N_g \varepsilon_1 \varepsilon_2}{J_r} + \varepsilon_2 \dot{\varepsilon}_2 \\ = & -K_1 \varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2 \left(\dot{\varepsilon}_2 - \frac{N_g \varepsilon_1}{J_r} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

To ensure the stability of \dot{V}_2 , let us set:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_2 - \frac{N_g \varepsilon_1}{J_r} = -K_2 \varepsilon_2 \quad (30)$$

Under this condition set, the following is achieved:

$$\dot{V}_2 = -K_1 \varepsilon_1^2 - K_2 \varepsilon_2^2 < 0 \quad (31)$$

which implies the asymptotic stability to the zero point. To conclude the reasoning, (28) and (30) are combined to obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{T}_{em} = & \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_r - J_g \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \dot{\omega}_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref} \\ & + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K \dot{\xi} + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K_1 \dot{\varepsilon}_1 + \frac{N_g \varepsilon_1}{J_r} - K_2 \varepsilon_2 \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

The control term T_{em} is obtained by integrating the last expression:

$$\begin{aligned} T_{em} = & \frac{T_a}{N_g} - \frac{K_r}{N_g} \omega_r - J_g \dot{\omega}_g - K_g \omega_g - \frac{J_r}{N_g} \dot{\omega}_{ref} \\ & + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K \xi + \frac{J_r}{N_g} K_1 \varepsilon_1 + \frac{N_g \xi}{J_r} - K_2 \int_0^t \varepsilon_2(\tau) d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

IB-SMC consists of two components, i.e.:

$$u_{IB-SMC} = T_{em} + u_{disc} \quad (34)$$

where T_{em} satisfies (32) and u_{disc} satisfies:

$$u_{disc} = -K \tanh\left(\frac{s}{\phi}\right) \quad (35)$$

SMC brings the benefit of fast-tracking for the desired trajectory. On the other hand, backstepping control brings the benefit of avoiding chattering and adding the integral term that ensures the system reaches zero steady-state error. As summarized in (33), IB-SMC brings into a unique setup the benefits of both SMC and integral backstepping control.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation of the proposed controller was divided into two parts: the first involves typical trajectory tracking without disturbances, while the second focuses on rotor speed tracking under external disturbances. Various control methods, including conventional control [49-50], SMC [51], I-SMC, and IB-SMC, were simulated to compare their tracking accuracy and robustness against external disturbances. IB-SMC was evaluated by simulating a two-mass wind turbine model in MATLAB/Simulink. It was a 600 kW CART3 variable-speed wind turbine model [15], and Table I details its variable-pitch characteristics.

A. Output Power Analysis

IB-SMC was compared with baseline, SMC, and I-SMC. The IB-SMC parameters were $K = 0.1$, $K_1 = 0.3$, and $K_2 = 0.0001$. The other methods were simulated with $K = 0.145$ and $K_i = 0.001$. The wind speed was kept the same in all experiments, according to the procedure described in [24], with a mean value of 8 m/s. Figure 1 shows the power produced by the wind turbine model using different control strategies. All control methods guided the model to its maximum power production, which varied greatly during short periods. To fairly grasp this information, the total amount of power produced was calculated for each control strategy. Table II summarizes the corresponding data, showing that IB-SMC outperformed all competitors, increasing efficiency by approximately 0.26% and proving the potential benefits of IB-SMC for wind turbines.

TABLE I. DATA FOR WIND TURBINE SIMULATIONS. VALUES USED IN THE SIMULATIONS

Symbol	Notation	Value	Units
R	Turbine rotor radius	21.65	M
ρ	Air density	1.225	kg/m ³
J_r	Rotoris inertial mass	3.25×10^5	kg.m ²
K_b	Shaft damping	9500	N.m/rad/s
B_b	Shaft stiffness	2.691×10^5	N.m/rad
K_r	Rotor's friction	27.36	N.m/rad/s
K_g	Generator friction	0.2	N.m/rad/s
J_g	Generator inertial mass	34.4	kg.m ²
T_a	Maximum electrical torque	3.753×10^5	N.m
N_g	Gearbox ratio	41.165	-
λ	Optimal tip ratio speed	8.5	-

TABLE II. POWER PRODUCTION UNDER DISTINCT CONTROL STRATEGIES

Criterion	Baseline	SMC	I-SMC	IB-SMC
P_{max} (kW)	218.33	218.31	218.27	218.91

B. Vibration Mitigation Analysis

Wind turbines are subjected to a wide range of vibrations, both from external and internal sources. The most significant external vibrations are caused by wind gusts and turbulence, which can cause the blades and the tower to shake and vibrate [53]. Internal vibrations can be caused by imbalances in the rotating components or other issues related to the support structures. In any case, excessive vibration can lead to fatigue and permanent damage to turbine components. In some circumstances, control can mitigate or amplify vibrations, as confirmed by simulations. Figure 2 shows that the IB-SMC

decreased the vibrations in the turbine model, in contrast to the other strategies that generated higher vibrations. This finding suggests that using IB-SMC to control wind turbines has the potential to protect the turbine mechanisms against vibrations.

C. Performance Comparison

The main control objective was to maximize power capture from the wind turbine by accurately tracking the rotor speed. Figure 3 shows the rotor speed for the following controllers: baseline, SMC, I-SMC, and IB-SMC. IB-SMC seems to track the optimal rotor speed, which is confirmed by the computed error shown in Table III. Figures 4 and 5 show the low-speed shaft torque and the electromagnetic torque response. IB-SMC showed lower oscillations when compared to SMC and I-SMC, however, the baseline seems to produce the lowest oscillations.

TABLE III. TRACKING ERROR OF THE ROTOR SPEED UNDER DISTINCT CONTROL STRATEGIES

Criterion	Baseline	SMC	I-SMC	IB-SMC
Error (%)	2.6	3.1	2.3	1

Table IV shows a comparison between the proposed and the conventional controllers. The following terms were used to compare the efficiency of the controllers: electrical efficiency (η_{elec}) and aerodynamic efficiency (η_{aero}). Aerodynamic efficiency is the ratio of energy captured by the wind turbine to the optimal energy available from the wind and can be mathematically expressed as:

$$\eta_{aero}(\%) = \frac{\int_{t_{ini}}^{t_{fin}} P_a(t) dt}{\int_{t_{ini}}^{t_{fin}} P_{aopt}(t) dt} \quad (36)$$

Electrical efficiency is the ratio of electric energy produced to the optimal energy available from the wind, and is given by:

$$\eta_{elec}(\%) = \frac{\int_{t_{ini}}^{t_{fin}} P_e(t) dt}{\int_{t_{ini}}^{t_{fin}} P_{aopt}(t) dt} \quad (37)$$

The optimal aerodynamic torque is given by:

$$P_{aopt} = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 C_{Pmax} v^3 \quad (38)$$

TABLE IV. COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT CONTROL STRATEGIES USING η_{elec} AND η_{aero}

Indicator	Baseline	SMC	I-SMC	IB-SMC
η_{elec} (%)	97.0	98.6	97.7	98.5
η_{aero} (%)	70.28	70.35	70.12	70.40
Max T_{em} (kNm)	1.625	1.626	1.627	1.642
Std T_{em} (kNm)	0.643	0.460	0.372	0.210

Figure 6 shows a variable wind profile with rapid peak changes [53], which was used to examine the effectiveness of the proposed controller. Figure 7 shows the rotor speed with a disturbance level of 5 kNm. The SMC and ISMC could not follow the reference rotor speed, resulting in a considerably reduced efficiency. In proportional control, the rotor speed deviates from the reference value and is influenced by all disturbance levels, while any adjustments on the pitch angle result in lower power than the intended rotor speed's extracted power value. The IB-SMC can adapt to the 10 kNm

disturbance level while maintaining the tracking of the desired rotor speed value. The main objective of the controllers is to maximize energy capture while reducing transmission stresses. The results show that the power captured from the reference rotor value remains almost unchanged for the IBSMC, even with a twofold increase in disturbance levels from 5 to 10 kNm. Unlike SMC and ISMC, power efficiency was affected by the 5 kNm disturbance, and proportional control was also influenced by disturbance and changes in pitch angle. Table V compares the performance and complexity of the controllers, showing that the baseline and SMC controllers have low complexity and performance. The I-SMC controller has low complexity and

moderate performance, which is consistent with [35]. The results indicate that the IB-SMC is the most complex and also the most effective controller among the four.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF ELECTROMAGNETIC TORQUE CONTROLLERS

Controller	Complexity	Performance
Baseline	Low	Low
SMC	Low	Low
I-SMC	Low	Moderate
IB-SMC	High	High

Fig. 1. Wind turbine simulation: power produced by distinct control strategies.

Fig. 2. Power spectral density of T_{16} : the greater the amplitude, the greater the vibration. IB-SMC seems to generate the lowest amplitude for most frequencies.

Fig. 3. Rotor speed comparison for SMC, I-SMC, and IB-SMC.

Fig. 4. Low-speed shaft torque comparison for SMC, I-SMC, and IB-SMC.

Fig. 5. Electromagnetic torque comparison for SMC, I-SMC, and IB-SMC.

Fig. 6. Wind speed profile.

Fig. 7. Rotor speed comparison for SMC, I-SMC, and IB-SMC with 5 kNm disturbance.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper introduced a novel control strategy for wind turbines termed as IB-SMC. This strategy combines the advantages of I-SMC, which facilitates tracking of the desired trajectory with backstepping control, which is known to prevent chattering and compensate for the steady-state error. In addition, IB-SMC ensures the stability of wind turbines. Comparative analysis was performed against the baseline, conventional SMC, and I-SMC, and simulation results showed that IB-SMC surpassed them in terms of power production, exhibiting an approximately 0.26% increase in efficiency. IB-SMC also demonstrated the ability to generate the lowest vibration amplitude in the turbine model, indicating its potential application to protect turbine mechanisms against vibrations. In conclusion, the simulations and result comparison underscored the potential advantages of the proposed IB-SMC strategy for wind turbines.

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A Novel Combination of Genetic Algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization, and Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization for Distribution Network Reconfiguration in Case of Faults

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ABSTRACT

Reconfiguring distribution networks involves modifying their topological structure by managing switch states. This process is crucial in smart grids, as it can isolate faults, minimize power loss, and enhance system stability. However, in existing research, the reconfiguration task is often treated as a problem of either single- or multi-objective optimization and frequently overlooks the issue's multimodality. As a result, the solutions derived may be inadequate or unfeasible when facing environmental changes. In this study, the objective function of minimizing power loss considers the case of faults in the distribution grid. Coordinating the initial population division of the Genetic Algorithm (GA) with the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and the Teaching and Learning-Based Optimization (TLBO) algorithms accelerates the process of finding the optimal solution, resulting in faster and more reliable results. The proposed method was tested on the IEEE-33 bus test system and was compared with other methods, demonstrating reliable results and superior efficiency.

Keywords-genetic algorithm; particle swarm optimization; teaching-learning-based optimization; reconfiguration distribution network; power loss reduction

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of industry and technology, distribution networks have become more complex due to the presence of dispersed energy sources and the diversity of load characteristics. An increase in the rate of incidents impacts electrical safety and customer satisfaction, as well as the economic benefits of electricity-selling enterprises. Reconfiguration of the distribution network in the event of an incident is an effective solution that involves adjusting the network configuration to ensure power supply and optimize economic operations [1-2]. Typically, the reconfiguration of distribution networks falls into two specific categories: (1) adjusting the distribution networks under standard conditions for better economic performance, and (2) reconfiguring distribution networks due to faults [3]. When faults occur, this reconfiguration involves altering the network's topological layout by modifying switch positions. In [4], the reconfiguration in response to faults in the distribution network was to boost its self-healing capacity. As such, this reconfiguration is vital for both elevating the system's reliability [5] and optimizing power flow distribution [6-7]. While it poses a complex optimization challenge, many research approaches address it as either a single-objective or multi-objective optimization task. In [8], a reconfiguration

model was developed for distribution networks under fault conditions, aiming to reduce power losses in the grid. A Genetic Algorithm (GA) with an enhanced mutation process was employed to address the reconfiguration issue when faults occur, and its results were validated using the IEEE 33-node distribution system. In [9], a multi-objective reconfiguration challenge was put forth for the electrical distribution network. Following that, an improved multi-objective evolutionary algorithm, grounded in Bayesian probabilistic learning, was utilized to tackle the highlighted challenge.

In [10], the Root Running Algorithm (RRA) was proposed to address the Distribution Network Reconfiguration (DNR) issue. This algorithm incorporates random jumping steps and reinitialization strategies to prevent falling into local minima, and simulation results highlighted its remarkable efficacy in tackling the DNR problem. Many studies leveraged GA to optimize network configurations to reduce losses and switching operations [11]. Alternative metaheuristic algorithms, such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), have been introduced to address this and enhance solution quality, especially to evade local optima. PSO has shown notable success in optimization, directing a population of particles using historical performance data. Its applications in DNR are varied, from enhancing load balancing to quality-performance trade-offs. In [12-13], a discrete PSO algorithm was proposed for DNR, noting its

computational intensity due to nonradial solutions. In [14-16], GA was utilized to decrease power loss and enhance electrical system reliability. Despite GA's proficiency with discrete variables and nonlinear objectives, its time efficiency remains a concern, and not all problems are amenable to GA solutions. Enhanced PSO variants have been developed to accelerate the search by incorporating historical solutions [17]. In [18], the Niche-Binary PSO (NBPSO) aims to avoid the issue of premature convergence endemic to standard PSO [19]. In [20], binary PSO was explored. In [21-23], artificial neural networks were used to optimize power loss. In [24], the gravitational optimization algorithm was used for the reconfiguration problem with multi-objective goals, such as reducing losses and operational costs. The reconfiguration process impacts not only power losses but also several other aspects of the distribution network. In [25], an enhanced heuristic method based on the branch exchange technique was utilized to address the problem, aiming to reduce loss costs, switch operation costs, and improve node voltage levels. The branch exchange method was refined to consistently produce valid network configurations without the need to solve the closed-network power distribution problem. In [26], a multi-objective heuristic method, the Fuzzy Multiobjective Approach (FMA), was introduced to target loss reduction, voltage deviation, and load balance across branches and feeders. Furthermore, some studies successfully employed generic heuristic algorithms for multi-objective reconfiguration, such as GA, and simulations demonstrated its ability to efficiently converge with a reduced population.

Unlike the previous studies, this one considers not only multi-objectives in the reconfiguration during distribution network incidents but also other objectives. As a result, solution outcomes might encompass multiple configurations to meet the problem's objectives, aiding operation engineers in selecting a distribution network structure to operate during malfunctions. However, local optimization and extended computation times pose challenges for numerous multi-objective evolutionary algorithms proposed in previous studies. Therefore, this issue continues to attract researchers' attention. To solve this problem, this study proposes an optimization method that combines the advantages of GA, PSO, and the Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization (TLBO) algorithm. The proposed technique was tested on the IEEE 33-node sample grid and compared with several other methods, demonstrating reliable results and improved computation speed.

II. MODEL AND CONSTRAINT CONDITIONS

The problem of reconfiguring the distribution grid in the event of a fault is a complex nonlinear optimization issue on a large scale and is dynamic due to the unpredictability of the fault location. Additionally, the objective function aims to reduce energy losses and voltage deviation errors, ensuring constraints on online loading capacity, power balance, and the radial operation of the distribution network.

A. The Objective Function

Based on [4, 8, 11], energy losses and voltage deviation errors are commonly used as objective functions in the

reconfiguration of distribution networks. These two objectives can help minimize system losses and maintain network stability. Therefore, energy losses and voltage deviation errors are the two objective functions. The objective function for power loss on the distribution network is given by:

$$F_1 = \min(\sum_{ij=1}^N k_{ij} R_{ij} \frac{P_{ij}^2 + Q_{ij}^2}{U_j^2}) \quad (1)$$

where N is the number of branches on the distribution network, k_{ij} is the status of the branch (k_{ij} equals 0 if the branch is open and 1 if it is closed), R_{ij} is the resistance of branch ij , P_{ij} is the active power on branch ij , Q_{ij} is the reactive power on branch ij , and U_j is the voltage at node j .

B. Constraint Conditions

The technical assurance conditions for distribution networks include the following:

Conditions to balance node active and reactive power:

$$P_{Gi} - P_{Si} - P_{di} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \Omega_b \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{Gi} - Q_{Si} - Q_{di} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \Omega_b \quad (3)$$

Condition to ensure allowable voltage limits:

$$U_{min} \leq U_i \leq U_{max} \quad \forall i \in \Omega_b \quad (4)$$

Condition to ensure current flow on branch ij :

$$I_{ij} \leq I_{ijmaxcp} \quad (5)$$

Condition to a radial structure for the distribution network:

$$h_k \leq H_k \quad (6)$$

where P_{Gi} is the active power generated at node i (pu), Q_{Gi} is the reactive power generated at node i (pu), P_{Si} is the total active power demanded at substation i (pu), Q_{Si} is the total reactive power demanded at substation i (pu), P_{di} is the total active power demanded at node i (pu), Q_{di} is the total reactive power demanded at node i (pu), Q_{Gi} is the reactive power generated at node i (pu), h_k is the restructured network structure, and H_k is the set of distribution grid structures that can be implemented according to the operating rules of the distribution network.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction to GA, PSO, and TLBO

1) Genetic Algorithm's (GA) Overview

GA was introduced as a stochastic search technique inspired by Darwin's theory of evolution [27]. GA is a probabilistic search method modeled on the principle of natural selection [13]. It initiates its search with a collection of population strings, each representing a potential solution within the predefined search domain. Mimicking biological evolution, GA generates new candidate solutions, termed offspring, from the preceding generation of parents. However, their exploratory capabilities can sometimes constrain GAs, resulting in slower convergence rates or suboptimal robustness [19]. This limitation makes them susceptible to premature convergence and entrapment in local optima, particularly in complex optimization scenarios.

2) Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Overview

PSO is a more recent addition to evolutionary computational techniques [28]. Drawing inspiration from the social behaviors of bird flocking or fish schooling, PSO features a group of particles, also known as potential solutions, that traverse the multi-dimensional solution space. The trajectory of each particle is influenced by its personal best position and the optimum found by its neighbors. Unlike GA, PSO employs the entire group of solutions from start to finish, adhering to the survival of the fittest doctrine. However, PSO shares similar drawbacks as GA, including issues with convergence speed and robustness.

3) Teaching-Learning Based Optimization (TLBO) Overview

TLBO is modeled after the interaction between a teacher and students in a classroom setting [29]. It encapsulates the concept of mutual learning, where individuals learn from a teacher and each other. TLBO is a population-based algorithm that views solution vectors as a class of students learning various subjects, analogous to manipulating different decision variables in an optimization problem. The algorithm employs two primary modes of learning: the teacher phase for global search, where the best solution acts as a teacher, and the learner phase for local search, where learners exchange knowledge among themselves. Through iterations, the population hypothesizes and converges toward the best global solution for the problem at hand.

4) Combining Algorithms

The flexibility of GA and PSO for nonlinear optimization problems has been analyzed and evaluated in many studies. Recent studies have indicated that a hybrid metaheuristic approach, integrating multiple strategies, is more effective than employing a single algorithm. This study introduces a GA-PSO-TLBO hybrid method, leveraging GA's global search capabilities, PSO's local search efficiency, and TLBO's learning mechanism, and validates its efficacy against conventional single and hybrid methods. The proposed method was used to solve the problem of minimizing power loss while electrical distribution networks are rearranging during faults. This study makes important contributions by introducing a useful hybrid metaheuristic approach and showing that it is robust, especially when investigating changes in population size and offspring generation in the TLBO process.

B. Combining GA-PSO-TLBO for the Reconfiguration Problem in Case of Fault

Applying a single optimization method to a problem is not as effective as leveraging the combined strengths of various optimization techniques [30]. This study proposes the GA-PSO-TLBO method to effectively address optimization problems with many discrete variables. The GA-PSO-TLBO method effectively combines the benefits of three different optimization techniques in its search process to enhance its problem-solving performance.

The GA method initiates its search by generating a random population. This population is made up of individuals with various fitness values, granting it global search capability. This ensures that the GA has a higher likelihood of identifying the

optimal solution compared to local search strategies such as SA and HC. However, since GA is rooted in a population-based search and utilizes operations (such as selection, crossover, and mutation) on the entire population, it may exhibit slower convergence tendencies [30]. To address this shortcoming of GA while still embracing a population-based search, an effective strategy could be to operate it on just a selected number of individuals rather than the whole group. This study used the top 50% of the initial population based on higher fitness values for the GA cycle. The rationale behind this is that leveraging the top 50% with higher fitness scores increases the probability of pinpointing the optimal solution compared to relying on those with lower fitness scores. The GA's search mechanism can counteract the potential issue of early convergence caused by significant similarities in the top-performing subset. The global search capability of GA serves to diversify the individuals in the group. On the contrary, using the subset with lower fitness values could reduce the probability of discovering the optimal solution [20]. This implies that if GA initiates its search with a population subset of lesser fitness values, it has a reduced chance of identifying the optimal solution. GA's approach of exploring a vast spectrum of values to boost individual diversity contributes to this. As a result, there is a pressing need to minimize the diversity within the subset that has lower fitness values to expedite the path to the optimal solution.

Implementing PSO in this lesser-performing group can be an effective strategy, given its ability to rapidly enhance the fitness values of current members based on their velocities and positions [20, 23]. This study uses the bottom 50% of the initial population based on lower fitness values for the PSO cycle. The reason behind this decision is that the PSO's search mechanism can enhance the fitness values of individuals in this subset, making the PSO a suitable method for swiftly pinpointing the optimal solution. Furthermore, it has been indicated [20, 23] that applying the TLBO search process to elite members following the GA search can lead to further enhancements. Given that GA does not provide substantial learning capabilities for its elite members during its search, introducing the TLBO search process to a select group with higher fitness scores can increase the probability of identifying the optimal solution. In this context, the top 50% of offspring, derived post-GA and PSO cycles, are used for the TLBO search phase. Figure 1 shows the flow chart of the proposed method. An initial population is randomly generated and divided into two subpopulations: 50% with higher fitness values and 50% with lower ones. These subpopulations are then fed into the GA and PSO loops, respectively. GA aims to diversify the population, while PSO aims to accelerate the search for the best solution. Integrating both GA and PSO boosts exploration and exploitation simultaneously. From the combined offspring of GA and PSO, 50% with higher fitness values are used in the TLBO loop, which aims to enhance the likelihood of pinpointing the optimal solution.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed algorithm was implemented in MATLAB 2019a, running on a PC with an i7 processor at 6 GHz, and applied to a 33-node distribution system. Comparative analysis

was performed based on distribution losses, node voltage values, fitness values, convergence iteration counts, and the time taken to execute the optimization process.

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the proposed GA- PSO-TLBO algorithm.

A. System Main Process

The main steps of the simulation process are executed as shown in Figure 3.

- Step 1: Update the operational parameters of the distribution network.
- Step 2: Simulate a fault at a location on the distribution network.
- Step 3: Identify the fault location and the nodes that are isolated (de-energized).
- Step 4: Update the distribution network parameters in the event of a fault.
- Step 5: Find the optimal configuration using the proposed GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm.
- Step 6: Calculate the established mode for the new configuration and check the constraint conditions.

```

Initialize the vector  $x_k$  as the state of the switches, where  $x_i$  has a value of 0 (switch open) or 1 (switch closed), following the formula:

$$x_k = \begin{matrix} x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m & x_{m+1}, x_{m+2}, \dots, x_n \\ \text{50\% for GA} & \text{50\% for PSO} \end{matrix}$$

Input: problem data  $(f(x), n)$ ,
parameters:  $maxGen, k, popSz, rand$ : random number);
output: the best solution  $G_{best}$ ;
begin:
 $t \leftarrow 0$ ;
randomly generate parent population  $P(t)=[x_k(t)]$ ;
evaluate  $P(t)$  and keep the best solution  $I_{best}$  in  $P(t)$ ;
while(not terminating condition)do
create  $P_1(t)$  using superior solutions (50%) from  $P(t)$ ;
// $P_1(t)=[x_{k/2}(t)]$ 
create  $P_2(t)$  using inferior solutions (50%) from  $P(t)$ ;
// $P_2(t)=[x_{k/2}(t)]$ 
create  $G(t+1)$  from  $P_1(t)$  by crossover routine;
// $G(t+1)=[x_{k/2}(t)]$ , GA population // GA loop
create  $G(t+1)$  from  $P_2(t)$  by mutation routine;
evaluate  $G(t+1)$  and keep the best solution  $GA_{best}$  in  $G(t+1)$ ;
 $PSO_{best} \leftarrow \text{big } M$ ; //PSO loop
for each particle  $x_k(t)$  in swarm of  $P_2(t)$  do
update velocity  $v_k(t)$  by  $v_k(t+1) = w \cdot v_k + c_1 d_1 (I_{best} - x_k) + c_2 d_2 (x_{best}(t) - x_k)$ ;
update position  $x_k(t+1)$  by  $x_k(t+1) = x_k(t) + v_k(t+1)$ ;
 $S(t+1) \leftarrow x_k(t+1)$ ; // $S(t+1)=[x_{k/2}(t)]$  //PSO population
if  $PSO_{best} > f(x_k(t+1))$  then
 $PSO_{best} = x_k(t+1)$ ;
end
end
create offspring using  $G(t+1)$  and  $S(t+1)$ ; //TLBO
create  $L(t+1)$  using 50% superior solutions from offspring; // $L(t+1)=[x_k(t)]$ , TLBO population
select teacher value  $X_{best}$  and calculate the mean of the class  $X_{mean}$  in  $L(t+1)$ ;
for  $k=1$  to  $popSz/2$ 
 $T_r = \text{round}(1 + \text{rand}(0,1))$  //Teacher phase
 $x_k(t+1)^{new} = x_k(t+1) + \text{rand}(X_{best} - T_r \cdot X_{mean})$ 
if  $f(x_k(t+1)) > f(x_k(t+1)^{new})$  then
 $x_k(t+1) = x_k(t+1)^{new}$ 
end
randomly select a learners  $x_p$  from  $\{1, 2, \dots, popSz\}$ ;
//Learner phase
if  $(x_k(t+1) > f(x_p))$  then
 $x_k(t+1)^{new} = x_k(t+1) + \text{rand}(x_k(t+1) - x_p)$ 
else
 $x_k(t+1)^{new} = x_k(t+1) - \text{rand}(x_k(t+1) - x_p)$ 
end
if  $f(x_k(t+1)) > f(x_k(t+1)^{new})$  then
 $x_k(t+1) = x_k(t+1)^{new}$ 
end
select  $X_{best}$  and calculate  $X_{mean}$  in  $L(t+1)$ ;
end
 $TLBO_{best} = X_{best}$ 
 $G_{best} = \text{argmin}\{I_{best}, GA_{best}, PSO_{best}, TLBO_{best}\}$ 
reproduce  $P(t+1)$  from  $G(t+1)$ ,  $S(t+1)$ , and  $L(t+1)$  by elitist selection routine;
 $t \leftarrow t+1$ ;
end
output: the best solution  $G_{best}$ 
end;
    
```

Fig. 2. The pseudocode of the proposed algorithm.

B. Parameter Setting of the IEEE-33 Bus

Figure 4 shows the IEEE-33 bus distribution system that was used to validate the performance of the GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm. The system consists of 33 nodes, 32 section switches, and 5 interconnection switches [11]. This system operates at a base voltage of 12.66 kV. In the initial state of the distribution network before any fault onset, switches 33-37 are open, while the rest remain closed. The initial power loss is 191 kW, with a voltage deviation of 0 pu [11]. The parameters of

the GA and PSO search align with those mentioned in [8]. For all algorithms, the maximum function evaluations and population size were set at 500 and 200, respectively.

Fig. 3. Steps to perform the simulation process.

Fig. 4. IEEE 33-bus distribution system and initial state.

C. Simulation Results

Identifying equivalent schemes is essential in the process of resolving fault reconfiguration issues within distribution networks. In this simulation, the efficacy of the GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm was demonstrated using the IEEE 33-bus distribution system framework. Table I proposes test scenarios during the occurrence of a fault in branch 9. Due to the fault at branch 9, nodes 9 to 17 are de-energized, resulting in their voltage values being zero before reconfiguration. After reconfiguration with the objective function aimed at reducing losses, Figure 5 shows that all previously de-energized nodes

were re-energized, the minimum node voltage increased, and the voltage quality of the power supply improved across all three considered schemes while maintaining voltage values within acceptable limits (0.9-1.1 pu). The losses associated with the proposed schemes were approximately equal. Based on the above analysis, the proposed method exhibits adaptability to dynamic or uncertain environments, and the equivalent solutions it provides can assist decision-makers in effectively managing unexpected faults, ensuring the completion of the distribution network's fault reconfiguration process without the need to adjust the initial objectives. This also improves the safety and reliability of the electrical supply in the distribution network. Furthermore, the proposed algorithm avoids local optima and offers three schemes that guarantee the satisfaction of the necessary constraints for the objective function and power supply capabilities.

TABLE I. RECONFIGURATION OF THE PROPOSED GA-PSO-TLBO

Case	Fault in branch	Solutions (switch open)	Power loss/100 kW	V _{min} /V _{max}
1	9	6;32;34;37	1.356	0.938/1.00
2	9	7;14;25;32	1.362	0.925/1.00
3	9	7;8;32;37	1.379	0.927/1.00

D. Comparison

Computational efficiency and algorithmic efficacy are important measures to solve real-world engineering challenges. Table II shows a comparison of the time the algorithms take to execute and the quality of the solutions they produce.

TABLE II. TIME AND NUMBER OF ITERATIONS COMPARISON

Case	GA-PSO-TLO (proposed)	SPEA [31]	MOPSO [32]	NSGA-II [33]
Time (s)	48.62	63.91	64.47	35.31
Number of iterations	42	40	39	36
Result	3	1	1	1

Table II consolidates the mean computational duration and the spectrum of solutions discerned by each algorithm. The proposed algorithm was faster than the Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimization (MOPSO) and the Strength Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm 2 (SPEA2). The proposed GA-PSO-TLBO method was also better than MOPSO and SPEA2 in finding a wider range of solutions. Although the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) had less runtime than the proposed one, it fell short in achieving its breadth in solution discovery. Table II shows that the proposed method is effective, accurate, and reliable. After careful consideration, it can be said that the GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm has a fast calculation speed, proposes optimal operating structures for the operator to choose from, and is therefore suitable for the problem of reconfiguring the distribution network in case of failure.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The optimization of fault reconfiguration processes is critical to improving the operational efficiency and

dependability of smart grid systems. This study presented the GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm, which combines discrete multimodal multi-objective PSO, GA, and TLBO.

Fig. 5. Reconfiguration schemes of equivalent solution: (a) initial state topology in branch 9, (b) reconfiguration case 1 for the equivalent solution, (c) reconfiguration case 2 for the equivalent solution, and (d) reconfiguration case 3 for the equivalent solution.

Fig. 6. Voltage values of each node equivalent solution.

This algorithm is specifically designed to address the complexities of fault reconfiguration in electrical distribution networks. This algorithm introduces a novel selection method to optimize the search for robust solutions within the GA-PSO-TLBO framework. The results, simulated in several fault cases, demonstrated that the precision of the proposed method is comparable to that of previous methods, but the convergence speed was enhanced, resulting in accelerated calculation times. The proposed algorithm generates more optimal configurations, which significantly aid decision-making in the operation of distribution networks during electrical faults. A comparative analysis was performed on an IEEE 33-bus against established methods, such as MOPSO, NSGA-II, and SPEA, to substantiate the algorithm's performance. The results showed that the proposed GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm was better suited to help with fault reconfiguration problems in distribution networks. In particular, the GA-PSO-TLBO algorithm excelled in generating a diverse array of feasible solutions in less time, providing decision-makers with a versatile toolkit to navigate emergencies and adapt to dynamic grid conditions.

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Voltage Control of a Three-Phase Distribution Grid using a DC Microgrid-Fed STATCOM

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ABSTRACT

With the increasing penetration of microgrids in distribution systems, the possibility for voltage variations increases. This paper proposes the use of a static synchronous compensator (STATCOM) fed by a DC microgrid to control the voltage of a 3-phase AC distribution grid and provide bidirectional active power transfer from the AC grid to the DC microgrid and vice versa. A simplified control is applied to this system to manage the magnitude and angle of the system voltage at the point of common coupling. With the use of a PI controller and pulse width modulation, the proposed control was able to modify the active and reactive power compensation. The control approach is characterized by its simplicity and rapid response to system changes, such as fault occurrences or load variations. The proposed control system is applied after converting the 3-phase system into a dq system to simplify the voltage regulation process. The PSCAD package is used to perform the simulation. Results demonstrate that it is possible to control STATCOM to offset reactive power and regulate grid voltage. The results validated the ability of active power transfer through the line by injecting negative and positive active power. The transfer of active and reactive power from the AC grid to the DC microgrid, and vice versa, is examined in this study following the STATCOM rating and the energy management demands.

Keywords-static synchronous compensator (STATCOM); PI controller; FACTS; DC microgrid

I. INTRODUCTION

Renewable energy is playing an important role in shaping the future of energy as a clean and sustainable source [1, 2]. Recently, the development of renewable energy generation has seen significant progress. The prevailing energy trend is

shifting towards renewable sources due to the advantages they offer, such as economic viability in various applications, ensured availability and sustainability, and environmental safety. Notable examples of renewable energy sources include photovoltaic (PV), wind, hydropower, tidal power, geothermal power, biomass power, and other systems [3].

In order to ensure the security of the energy supply, microgrids have emerged as a viable solution. A microgrid refers to a small-scale network that can independently supply power to loads, with or without assistance from the main grid [4]. A typical microgrid comprises batteries, loads, and interconnected renewable energy sources, all connected to the same bus. There are three main types of microgrids: DC, AC, and hybrid. Among these, the DC microgrid offers several advantages, including enhanced system stability, compact size, absence of synchronization, and reduced costs while using DC-based renewables and energy storage systems [5-7]. The AC distribution grid faces various power quality issues, such as voltage disturbances, harmonic distortion, unbalance among phases and low power factor. These problems not only disturb the normal operation of the system but also impact the performance of connected loads. Consequently, extensive studies have been carried out to address these issues and enhance the power quality of the grid through the utilization of power electronics-based devices, such as the Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS). The major types of FACTS devices are the static synchronous compensator (STATCOM) and the Static VAR Compensator (SVC). The response time of STATCOM is faster than SVC [8, 9]. In order to keep the grid voltage at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC) within a particular range, reactive power is compensated with STATCOM [10].

STATCOM is considered a very important device widely used in power systems for various applications. For compensating reactive power, the STATCOM is proposed in [11] using a model of half bridge and modular multilevel converter. In [12], D-STATCOM is proposed to be used to mitigate unbalanced voltage characteristics resulting from the connection of a three-phase transformer bank in a distribution system. In [13], three various strategies were proposed to control STATCOM by controlling the voltage and reactive power. In [14], a STATCOM is designed to improve the low-voltage ride-through capability of grid-connected induction machines following grid faults by controlling the reference voltage, thereby limiting the maximum torque of the induction motor. A comparison between SVC and STATCOM was carried out in [15], while the applications of STATCOM for power quality improvement of grid-connected wind farms were described in [16, 17]. In [18], a PID controller with an adaptive switched filter capacitor and a modified D-STATCOM were

proposed. The PID controller gains were optimally tuned using the grasshopper's optimization algorithm. A new mechanism is added in [19] as a secondary control to regulate the voltage of the DC-link. This mechanism is based on the magnitude of the modulation index and aims to keep the current total harmonic distortion within the standard range.

This paper proposes a new system aiming to provide voltage support for 3-phase AC grids through incorporating a STATCOM fed by a DC microgrid. The utilization of STATCOM facilitates the integration of the microgrid and the main grid and allows for precise control of the grid voltage. Also, the STATCOM regulates the active and reactive power flow between the main power grid and the microgrid. The main contributions of this article can be summarized as follows:

- A new structure for voltage support in 3-phase distribution grids using a DC microgrid interfaced via STATCOM is introduced.
- A decoupling control method for active and reactive power exchange between the grid and the microgrid is developed, in contradiction to previous studies which focused only on reactive power control.
- The proposed structure and control are validated in a real-time platform.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The system consists of the AC grid, the STATCOM and a DC microgrid. Figure 1 illustrates the connection between the grid and the microgrid through STATCOM. A 3-phase star-earthed transformer is utilized to establish the connection between STATCOM and the AC grid. A 3-phase load is applied to the AC grid, with the load becoming operational after 5 s. An inductance is added between the PCC and the output of the transformer. In general, STATCOM consists of an inverter and a capacitor located in the DC link. The inverter consists of 6 Insulated-Gate Bipolar Transistors (IGBTs) designed to turn on and off rapidly. In this work, the microgrid is located on the DC link instead of the conventional capacitor. The microgrid, as depicted in Figure 2 [20], encompasses a PV system, a wind turbine system, two batteries, and loads. The 3-phase transformer is installed to connect between the two various voltage levels of the AC grid and the inverter's AC side.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed system.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the studied microgrid.

III. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION OF STATCOM

In the family of FACTS electronic components, STATCOM is a key component that is shunt connected with the system. A power network's stability is boosted by STATCOM's capacity to control the flow of reactive power through the system. The term "synchronous" in STATCOM refers to the ability to generate or absorb reactive power in time with the need to maintain the power network's voltage. The 3-phase AC power grid system was studied in this work. The type of power electronic switches of the inverter is IGBT. The advantages of IGBT over others are that the IGBT has high power density, small size, high reliability, and low cost [21].

Figure 3 shows the characteristic curve of an STATCOM. STATCOM is regarded as an inductive or capacitive current source. According to the power system parameters and the slope of the STATCOM parameters, the injected current can modify the voltage of the PCC. The maximum capacitive or inductive current limits can be determined using STATCOM component ratings. Due to the brief duration of transient events, the transient ratings are slightly higher than the nominal ratings. An example of how the STATCOM can adjust the PCC voltage by reactive power compensation is illustrated in Figure 4. Reactive power compensation needs a certain value of capacitor current to adjust the grid voltage at the reference value. If the value of system voltage V_s is reduced to 0.7 pu, the line characteristics of the system intersect with the characteristics of STATCOM at point X which refers to X_1 , corresponding to capacitor current I_x . The value of X_1 (about 0.95 pu) closes to the reference voltage of 1 pu. This improvement of voltage is due to the capacitor current I_x and reactive power compensator [22, 23]. Figure 5 shows the schematic diagram of the STATCOM device, where the STATCOM is represented by the inverter and the capacitor. It is connected to the power grid through an impedance consisting of both resistance and inductance [23]. The equivalent circuit of the STATCOM, as depicted in Figure 6, comprises two voltage sources. The AC voltage source represents the grid, while the controlled voltage source E_{dc} represents the STATCOM. The impedance between these two voltage sources includes both resistance and inductance. Assuming negligible internal losses in the link between the voltage sources V_s and E_{dc} , the resistance R can be considered as being equal to 0. The

active and reactive power flowing through the line are determined by:

$$P = \frac{V_s E_{dc} \sin \delta}{X} \tag{1}$$

$$Q = \frac{E_{dc} (V_s \cos \delta - E_{dc})}{X} \tag{2}$$

where V_s is the AC voltage source of the grid, E_{dc} is the DC voltage source on the capacitor, and δ is the load angle between V_s and E_{dc} .

Fig. 3. Characteristic curve of the STATCOM.

Fig. 4. Example of STATCOM operation and adjustment.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of the STATCOM device.

Fig. 6. Equivalent circuit of the STATCOM device.

When the load angle δ equals to 0, the transferred active power P and reactive power Q can be determined by:

$$P = 0 \tag{3}$$

$$Q = \frac{E_{dc} (V_s - E_{dc})}{X} \tag{4}$$

The previous equations explain the relation between the reactive power and the magnitude of the voltage and the relation between the active power and the angle. STATCOM operates on this guiding idea [24]. The formulation of a specific magnitude of voltage E_{dc} determines how STATCOM controls the reactive power flow via the line. Also, active power can be transferred through the system.

IV. VOLTAGE CONTROL OF STATCOM CONNECTED TO THE MICROGRID AT THE DC SIDE

The goal in this study is to maintain a constant value for the 3-phase voltage of the AC system at the PCC. Another goal is to regulate the active power flow between the grid and the DC system based on energy management requirements. The control method proposed in this study is presented in Figure 7, which consists of three steps. In the first step, the 3-phase voltage of the grid is converted into a simplified 2-phase system. This conversion is performed to facilitate the control process. The second step involves applying the control method to the newly obtained 2-phase system. Finally, in the third step, the 2-phase system is transformed back into a 3-phase system to enable the application of Pulse Width Modulation (PWM).

In Figure 7, the grid voltage (V_{ag} , V_{bg} , and V_{cg}) is converted into a dq0 rotating reference frame (V_d , V_q , and V_0). This transformation to the dq0 frame is crucial because it simplifies the control process by decoupling the control of two axes. V_q is responsible for adjusting the reactive power and consequently the voltage, while V_d is responsible for regulating the active power and hence the phase difference (δ). The equations of converting abc axes to dq0 axes are:

$$V_d = \frac{2}{3} (V_{ag} \sin(\omega t) + V_{bg} \sin(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) + V_{cg} \sin(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3})) \tag{5}$$

$$V_q = \frac{2}{3} (V_{ag} \cos(\omega t) + V_{bg} \cos(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) + V_{cg} \cos(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3})) \tag{6}$$

$$V_0 = \frac{1}{3} (V_{ag} + V_{bg} + V_{cg}) \tag{7}$$

where V_d , V_q , and V_0 represent the output voltage from converting abc to dq0 and V_{ag} , V_{bg} , and V_{cg} represent the voltage of the grid system at the PCC of phases A, B and C.

The PI controller is used to control V_d and V_q . The PI controller coefficients are: integral time constant of 0.005 s and

proportional gain of 10. The output signals of the controller V_{d1} and V_{q1} are converted from dq0 (V_{d1} and V_{q1}) to abc (V_{aa} , V_{ab} and V_{ac}). The conversion from dq0 axes to abc axes is shown in (8)-(10). The signals V_{aa} , V_{ab} and V_{ac} are the inputs to PWM used to control the six IGBT signals as given in Figure 8. The input signals to the PWM device are the 3-phase outputs from the dq0/abc device. The PWM device compares these 3-phase signals and triangle functions to obtain the control signals for the gates of the IGBT devices that are responsible for controlling the grid voltage. Control and PWM are simulated in the PSCAD package. For controlling the voltage, V_{qref} will be adjusted to the reference value that controls the reactive power transfer in the system and therefore the voltage of the system. V_{dref} will be adjusted to the reference value that controls the active power transfer in the system and therefore the angle of the system.

$$V_{aa} = V_{d1} \sin(\omega t) + V_{q1} \cos(\omega t) + V_0 \tag{8}$$

$$V_{ab} = V_{d1} \sin(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) + V_{q1} \cos(\omega t - \frac{2\pi}{3}) + V_0 \tag{9}$$

$$V_{ac} = V_{d1} \sin(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) + V_{q1} \cos(\omega t + \frac{2\pi}{3}) + V_0 \tag{10}$$

Fig. 7. Proposed control structure of the STATCOM.

Fig. 8. Pulse generation block for STATCOM IGBTs.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

The PSCAD program was utilized to simulate the proposed system. This system consists of an AC grid, a DC microgrid, and the STATCOM. The AC 3-phase system parameters are as follows: rated line voltage 11 kV, rated frequency 50 Hz, and Thevenin equivalent internal reactance 28.27 Ω . For current limiting purposes and adjusting the reactive and active power

transfer, a reactor with an inductance of 1.1 H is added between the PCC and the transformer. The DC microgrid has a voltage of 380 V. The microgrid system consists of a PV system with a maximum power of 60 kW, 4 wind models connected in parallel with a maximum power of 10 kW, 2 batteries with maximum power of 40 and 20 kW, and static loads with power of 80 kW. The transformation ratio of the transformer is set at 30 kV/380 V.

The STATCOM is operated to improve and keep the AC grid voltage at a constant value or near to the reference voltage and allow the transition of active power from and to the grid. In the event of a system disturbance causing a change in grid voltage, the STATCOM will be activated to restore and stabilize the voltage, bringing it back or close to the reference value. Three cases will be studied in which three loads will be added on the grid side after 5 s by using a circuit breaker. At first, the system operates in stable mode at 11 kV. Then, the load will enter the system and change the grid voltage. Finally, the STATCOM control will operate and enhance the system and bring back the grid voltage to 11 kV. The results will compare the grid voltage with the reference voltage. In two of the considered cases, the load causes a decrease in the grid voltage below 11 kV, while in the third case, the load leads to an increase in the grid voltage beyond 11 kV.

The first case, illustrated in Figure 9, involves the addition of an inductive load of 285 kVAR after the grid. Initially, the grid voltage starts at a steady state voltage of 11 kV. After 5 s, the grid voltage decreases to 10.3 kV. However, the control system eventually restores the voltage close to the reference value. Figure 10 depicts the second case where an inductive load of 135 kVAR is added to the grid at 5 s. Initially, the grid voltage starts at a steady state voltage of 11 kV. After 5 s, the grid voltage decreased to 10.65 kV. Subsequently, the control system restores the voltage back to the reference value. Figure 11 illustrates the third case where a capacitive load of 135 kVAR is added to the grid after 5 s. Similar to the previous case, the grid voltage begins at the steady state voltage of 11 kV. After 5 s, the grid voltage increases to 11.3 kV. Once again, the control system intervenes to bring the voltage back to the reference value.

Fig. 9. Grid and reference voltage for inductive load of 285 kVAR.

Fig. 10. Grid and reference voltage for inductive load of 135 kVAR.

Fig. 11. Grid and reference voltage for capacitive load 135 kVAR.

In the first case, the grid voltage is improved but remains slightly below 11 kV due to the substantial difference between the grid voltage and the reference voltage. However, in the second and third cases, the grid voltage is successfully improved to 11 kV. The improvement in the voltage depends on reactive power. When the grid voltage reduces, the grid absorbs a certain amount of reactive power to compensate for the reduction of the voltage. When the grid voltage increases, the grid gives a certain amount of reactive power to compensate for that increase. The capacity of the microgrid determines its capability to provide reactive power support. Table I illustrates the value of reactive power compensation for the considered cases. It is evident that when the grid voltage is less than the reference voltage, the grid absorbs reactive power. This results in a negative value of reactive power, as illustrated in cases 1 and 2. Conversely, when the grid voltage surpasses the reference voltage, the grid supplies reactive power, leading to a positive value of reactive power, as seen in case 3. It is worth noting the discrepancy in the reactive power values between cases 1 and 2. In case 1, where there is a larger difference between the grid voltage and the reference voltage, the absorption of reactive power is greater than in case 2.

The system described here effectively facilitates the transfer of active power between the grid and the microgrid during both steady-state and transient conditions. The injection or absorption of 20 kW active power in the three cases is presented in Figures 12 and 13. Figure 12 displays the results of the microgrid's DC current for the three cases when active power is injected from the grid, resulting in a positive DC current. Figure 13 shows the DC current for the three cases

when the grid absorbs active power. In this scenario, the DC current of the microgrid becomes negative since the grid is drawing active power from the microgrid. Notably, the DC current value in case 1 is higher than that in case 2. This discrepancy is attributed to the varying load conditions in the two cases. When the load is larger, the DC current tends to be higher, and vice versa.

Fig. 12. The microgrid's DC current when active power is injected from the grid.

Fig. 13. The microgrid's DC current when the grid absorbs active power.

TABLE I. GRID VOLTAGE AND REACTIVE POWER

Cases	Load	Grid voltage	Reactive power
1	285 kVAR	10.3 kV	-60 kVAR
2	135 kVAR	10.65 kV	-50 kVAR
3	-135 kVAR	11.3 kV	45 kVAR

VI. REAL-TIME IMPLEMENTATION OF THE SYSTEM ON HIL PLATFORM

Typhoon HIL402 is a Hardware-In-the-Loop (HIL) real-time emulator that is frequently used for the design, testing, and test automation of power electronics control systems. Typhoon HIL platform is a valuable tool for validating the operation of the system. It contains a schematic editor that allows modeling and simulating the proposed system and controller. Typhoon HIL SCADA is a straightforward, user-friendly graphical environment that enables users to design custom interfaces with real-time models. The HIL SCADA program does two main tasks: it downloads simulation models to the HIL platform, and

it manages the parameters, output, and emulation process. Many applications are performed on the HIL platform, such as the control development stage, automated converter controller testing, system integration stage, and interoperability testing.

Figure 14 shows the proposed system applied in the schematic editor of the HIL program. The system contains a 3-phase grid, a 3-phase transformer, a 3-phase converter, and a DC link. The objective of this system is to enhance the grid voltage and maintain it at its reference value. The 3-phase grid is star-earthed, and its specific details are provided in Table II. The 3-phase transformer is also star-earthed on both primary and secondary sides and has a transformation ratio of 40 kV/380 V. To manipulate the electrical signals by modifying, restructuring, or eliminating undesirable high frequencies, a 3-phase T-type low-pass filter is connected after the transformer, having $L_2 = 0.009$ mH, $C_1 = 0.01$ μ F, and $L_3 = 0.1$ mH. The STATCOM, which consists of the 3-phase converter and the DC link, is also a part of the system. The 3-phase converter is controlled by a controller that regulates the voltage value, and it is equipped with 6 gates. The DC link is powered by a 380 V battery.

Figure 15 displays a visual representation of the testing setup for the proposed system, incorporating the HIL402 kit and a breakout board. To model the control circuits, the schematic editor within the Typhoon HIL control center is employed.

Figure 16 illustrates the control of the system. The Phase-Locked Loop (PLL) is used to obtain the value of ωt and convert the 3-phase voltage into the dq frame. The PLL device has the same frequency as the system (50 Hz). The inputs to PLL are the instantaneous values of 3-phase voltage at PCC. The outputs of PLL are the voltages of the dq frame (V_d , V_q , and V_0) as shown in (5)-(7), the frequency (F), ωt , and $\sin(\omega t)$. Frequency and $\sin(\omega t)$ are connected to termination because they were not used. In the HIL program, V_d represents the reactive power and V_q represents the active power. To improve the voltage, reactive power compensation is proposed. So, V_d is compared with the reference voltage and the error enters the PI controller as input and V_{d1} is obtained. Active power did not improve the voltage. So, V_q was compared to zero and the error entered the PI controller to obtain V_{q1} . The PI controller was adjusted at integral time constant (K_i) of 0.3 s and proportional gain (k_p) of 11. The outputs of the PI controller entered the dq0/abc device to convert the dq frame to abc frame as shown in (8)-(10). This device has a ωt input with the same value as PLL. The waves from this device (V_{aa} , V_{ab} , and V_{ac}) are used to do PWM.

PWM is an effective technique used to divide an electrical signal into discrete portions, thereby reducing the average power delivered. This is achieved by rapidly switching the supply and load on and off, allowing for precise control over the average voltage and current delivered to the load. The simplest method for generating a PWM signal is the intersective approach, which involves using a triangle waveform (easily generated with a triangle generator) and a comparator device. Figure 17 illustrates this process, with the triangle generator producing a signal value of 8000 Hz.

Fig. 14. The proposed system on Typhoon HIL 402.

Fig. 15. Picture of the system implementation configuration based on Typhoon HIL 402.

overview and facilitate easy comparison, Table III summarizes the main features and characteristics of all relevant methods, including our system. This table highlights the strengths of the proposed system over the existing techniques.

Fig. 16. Control structure of STATCOM.

TABLE II. GRID DETAILS

	Phase A	Phase B	Phase C
Line to line voltage	11 kV	11 kV	11 kV
Frequency	50 Hz	50 Hz	50 Hz
Phase angle	0 deg	-120 deg	120 deg
Internal inductance L_1	0.09 H	0.09 H	0.09 H

The system's results involve a comparison between the line voltage of the grid and the reference line voltage of 11 kV. These measurements were conducted under three different load conditions: an inductive load of 285 kVAR, an inductive load of 135 kVAR, and a capacitive load of 135 kVAR. The corresponding data are depicted in Figures 18-20. The results indicate that initially, the line voltage of the grid varies, but the control mechanism adjusts it to match the reference voltage.

The findings of this study highlight the significant advantages offered by the proposed system compared to previous research in the field. To provide a comprehensive

Fig. 17. PWM in Typhoon HIL device.

Fig. 18. Grid and reference voltage for inductive load of 285 kVAR.

Fig. 19. Grid and reference voltage for inductive load of 135 kVAR.

Fig. 20. Grid and reference voltage for capacitive load of 135 kVAR.

TABLE III. COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN THE PROPOSED SYSTEM AND THE EXISTING LITERATURE

Ref.	Multiple energy sources	Reactive power control	Active power control	Control method / complexity	Real-time validation
[8]	X	√	√	PI controller / Medium	X
[25]	√	√	√	Fuzzy-based / High	X
[26]	X	√	X	PI controller / Low	√
[27]	√	√	X	Neuro-Fuzzy / High	X
[28]	√	√	X	PI controller / Low	√
[29]	√	√	X	Genetic and Bacteria Foraging Algorithms / High	X
[30]	X	√	√	PI controller / Low	X
[31]	X	√	√	PI controller / Medium	X
Proposed	√	√	√	PI controller / Low	√

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes the use of STATCOM to connect an AC grid with a line voltage of 11 kV and a 380 V DC microgrid. The aim of this paper is to control the grid voltage at various conditions. To control the 3-phase system, at first the 3-

phase system is converted to a dq system, then the control is applied on the dq system. STATCOM controls the reactive power compensation in order to control the grid voltage. The amount of injection of negative or positive reactive power depends on the difference between the grid voltage and the reference voltage. The system was simulated in the PSCAD package. The results of voltage are taken at three various cases of load at the common coupling point. In the first two cases, inductive load was added, decreasing the grid voltage below the reference voltage. In the third case, capacitive load was added, increasing the grid voltage higher than the reference voltage. The STATCOM control improved the grid voltage to its reference value. The proposed system also allows the transfer of the active power from and to the AC grid. The transition of active power is shown by studying the value of DC current at 0, 20, and -20 kW of active power transfer. At zero active power, the average DC current is approximately equal to zero. At the transition of 20 kW of active power, the average DC current is positive value. At -20 kW transition of active power, the average DC current is negative value. DC current is approximately equal to 500 A. At -50 kW transition of active power, the average DC current is approximately equal to -500 A. Finally, a real-time experiment was conducted and the results proved the effectiveness of the proposed control system.

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Comparative Studies on Load Frequency Control with Different Governors connected to Mini Hydro Power Plant via PSCAD Software

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ABSTRACT

Mini Hydropower Plants (MHPPs) are increasingly popular for rural electrification in developing nations due to their ecologically friendly operation. However, constant load fluctuation in these facilities poses a speed control issue. The mechanical, hydraulic governor, commonly used to face this challenge, cannot provide the best speed control due to its mechanical component system. Thus, an electrohydraulic PID-based governor is proposed to control the frequency and speed of MHPPs in a distribution network. This governor's suitability for regulating the system's frequency in response to significant load variations within the distribution network is going to be determined in this study. The small hydropower plant and distribution system are modeled using the PSCAD software. A comparison between the mechanical hydraulic governor and the electro-PID governor was conducted by analyzing load fluctuations between 5% and 20%. The electro-PID governor responded faster and more actively to load connections and disconnections than the mechanical hydraulic governor, as the latter reduces large overshoots and undershoots, which can be dangerous and damaging to equipment. The electro-PID governor also helps to maintain a stable frequency within acceptable limits, ensuring smooth operation and minimizing the risk of system failures or disruptions.

Keywords-control; energy; frequency; hydro governor; load; renewable energy sources

I. INTRODUCTION

Load frequency control is a crucial aspect of power systems as it ensures the stability and reliability of the grid. By

continuously monitoring and adjusting the generation and load balance, the former helps maintain a steady frequency within acceptable limits. This is vital to prevent power outages,

equipment damage, and disruptions in electricity supply, ultimately ensuring the smooth functioning of various industries and meeting consumers' energy demands [1]. Governors play a significant role in load frequency control as they help prevent frequency fluctuations and ensure the efficient operation of power systems [2]. In the context of comparative studies on load frequency control involving different governors, connected with mini hydro power, it is important to analyze the performance and effectiveness of various governor types in maintaining frequency stability. Understanding how different governors respond to load changes and their ability to prevent frequency fluctuations, will provide valuable insights for optimizing the operation of mini hydro power systems [3]. These systems are popular for generating renewable energy, especially in remote areas. Therefore, studying the performance of different governor types in mini hydro power systems is essential for maximizing their efficacy and minimizing frequency fluctuations [4]. Mini hydro power refers to the generation of electricity using small-scale hydroelectric systems, typically with a capacity of less than 10 MW. It provides a sustainable source of electricity, particularly in remote areas where grid connectivity is limited or non-existent [5]. Mini hydro power systems can also contribute to load frequency control in power generation. Load frequency control refers to the regulation of power output to match the varying demand for electricity [6]. These systems must be able to quickly detect changes in demand and adjust their output accordingly to maintain a stable frequency.

Proper coordination and communication between multiple Mini Hydro Power Plants (MHPPs) within a grid is essential to ensure balanced load sharing and prevent frequency deviations [2]. Governors play a crucial role in load frequency control for mini hydro power systems. Proper calibration and maintenance of governors is necessary to ensure accurate and reliable frequency control. Additionally, advanced control algorithms and technologies can be implemented to optimize governors' performance and enhance load frequency control in mini hydro power systems [7]. Governors are mechanical or electronic devices that regulate the speed and power output of turbines in power systems [8]. Two main types of governors are used in mini hydro power systems: mechanical and electronic. Mechanical governors use mechanical components such as flyweights and springs to control the water flow and maintain a stable frequency. Both types of governors play a crucial role in optimizing the performance of mini hydro power systems by ensuring efficient load frequency control [9]. Governors in load frequency control are responsible for maintaining a stable frequency by adjusting the water flow to the turbine. This is crucial because any deviation in frequency can lead to disruptions in the power supply and potentially damage electrical equipment. By continuously monitoring and adjusting the turbine speed and power output, governors help regulate the balance between power generation and load demand, ensuring system stability and preventing blackouts or brownouts [10]. By comparing the performance of governors in different systems, researchers can identify the most suitable approaches for load frequency control, leading to improved power system reliability and efficiency [11]. This review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the various governor types

used in MHPPs and their impact on load frequency control. It will also aid in identifying possible areas for additional research and advancement in this sector [12]. Furthermore, the analysis of comparative studies will enable a comprehensive understanding of each governor type strengths and weaknesses, facilitating the implementation of informed choices in MHPPs [13].

The system's frequency and voltage exhibit synchronous fluctuations in response to changes in load, which result from a delayed response in load demand balancing. These power plants employ diverse control systems to maintain the frequency and voltage within acceptable limits [14]. A new adaptive scheme to avoid miscoordination associated with recloser-fuse protection of distribution network under distributed generation insertion is explored in [15]. MHG control technique is older and comprises of both hydraulic and mechanical components. Since electric components perform better and are more flexible than mechanical components, modern hydraulic turbine governors use electro-hydraulic systems [16]. The PID controller that comes with these electro-hydraulic governors is called an electro-hydraulic based PID governor, and it regulates the system frequency during significant load fluctuations. It responds faster and performs better than a hydraulic governor with a mechanical foundation. The proportionate term (P) handles the current control. Error and integral term (I) address past control errors, while derivative term (D) addresses potential future control errors [17]. The goal of this effort is to identify an appropriate governor that will stabilize the system following a significant load variation. In order to do this, a distribution test network that is linked to a MHPP of the Distributed Generation (DG) type is taken into consideration. The primary goals of this endeavor are:

- To use the PSCAD/EMTDC software to model the mechanical hydraulic governor and the electro-hydraulic PID based governor for the micro hydro power plant's load frequency regulation.
- To demonstrate the efficacy of both governors and compare their responses for load frequency control under various load fluctuation scenarios.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Distributed Generation

DG refers to the generation of electricity from small-scale power sources that are located close to the point of use. These power sources can include renewable energy technologies, such as solar panels, wind turbines, and micro-hydro systems, as well as conventional fossil fuel-based generators. DG offers numerous benefits, including increased energy efficiency, reduced transmission losses, and improved grid reliability [18]. Additionally, DG promotes energy independence and empowers communities to generate their own clean energy, fostering sustainability and reducing reliance on fossil fuels [19].

B. Types of Distributed Generation

DGs include solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, wind turbines, biomass generators, fuel cells, and microturbines.

These technologies enable electricity production either at or near the consumption point, reducing transmission and distribution losses and increasing overall system efficiency. Each DG technology type has its own unique advantages and considerations, making it important for policymakers and stakeholders to understand their characteristics and potential applications in order to effectively incorporate them into the energy landscape [20]. DG systems can be expensive to install and maintain, requiring significant upfront investment. They may also face regulatory barriers and challenges during their integration with existing grid infrastructure [21]. Firstly, DG systems have the ability to operate independently from the main grid, providing a reliable power source during grid

failures or emergencies. Additionally, DG systems can be more competent in terms of energy transmission as they are located closer to the end-users, reducing transmission losses that occur in centralized power generation [22]. The distributed generation technologies can be categorized as shown in Figure 1. Distributed generation refers to the production of electricity from multiple small-scale power sources located near the end-users. These sources can include renewable energy technologies, such as solar panels, wind turbines, and fuel cells, as well as conventional generators. The technical aspects of distributed generation involve various considerations, namely system integration, power quality, grid interconnection, and control strategies [23].

Fig. 1. Distributed generation and source classification.

1) DG Operation Mode

DG or premeditated islanded mode [24] operation refers to the process of generating electricity at various smaller-scale locations, like homes or businesses, rather than relying solely on centralized power plants. This decentralized approach allows for greater flexibility and reliability in the power grid, as well as increased energy efficiency.

2) Mini Hydro Power Plant

An MHPP is a small-scale hydroelectric power station that harnesses the energy of flowing or falling water to generate electricity. These plants are typically designed to have a capacity of less than 10 MW and are often located in rural or remote areas where access to larger power grids may be limited. They provide a sustainable and renewable energy source, contributing to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and promoting local economic development [25].

a) Working Principle of a Mini Hydro Power Plant Type DG

MHPPs work by utilizing the water flow from a natural source, such as a river or stream, to generate electricity through the use of turbines and generators. Control systems ensure the effective operation and monitoring of these components, optimizing power generation from the available water flow [26]. The advantages of implementing MHPPs include their lower environmental impact, as they require smaller dams and reservoirs compared to larger-scale installations. Additionally, considering factors such as water flow rate, available land area,

and environmental impact is crucial in assessing the viability of MHPPs [27]. Figure 2 displays the block diagram for the MHPP islanded mode of operation.

Fig. 2. MHPP islanded mode of operation.

Traditionally, mechanical hydraulic PI and PID governors as well as electro-hydraulic governors have been used to regulate speed. PID controllers are perfect for governor control since they have three different system management methods. Owing to its proportional, integral, and derivative functions—which, in turn, reduce rising time, zero steady state error, and reduced oscillation—the system may respond swiftly to load perturbations. PID and PI controls are excellent for second-order systems and operate well with linear models. One such instance in which he controlled a prototype micro hydropower plant's load frequency using the PI controller technique is described in [28]. Although PID controllers offer many advantages, they struggle to reach the optimal degree of

parameter adjustment. PID controllers are unable to offer satisfactory control over non-linear systems that have a severe integrator wind-up problem [29]. The suggested technique is called the Maximum Peak Resonance Specifications (MPRS) methodology. A predefined bandwidth and phase margin provide system stability [30]. In comparison to conventional PI controllers, this controller's dynamics and stability have shown enhanced power system dampening and better performance [31].

b) Electro-Hydraulic PID Governor Functionality

Electro-Hydraulic PID governors use electric hydraulic systems. Functionally, their operation is very similar to that of mechanical-hydraulic governors, but:

- Electrical systems are employed in many computation and measurement activities, including speed detection and both permanent and temporary droop.
- Electric components provide greater flexibility and improved performance in terms of dead bands and time lags.
- The dynamic features of a PID governor are usually adjusted to mimic those of a mechanical hydraulic governor.

c) Alternative Control Techniques

Several alternative control strategies have been suggested, in addition to conventional techniques, to stabilize frequency fluctuations. One strategy to reduce frequency variation is to use ballast or dump loads [32]. To distribute the load and protect the generator, dump loads need high resistors. A dump load's operation can be controlled with an Electronic Load Governor (ELG). The ELG is composed of an electrical device that automatically adjusts the ratio between the real Load and the dump load in order to maintain a constant load on the generator. Figure 3 illustrates the dump load and ballast concept.

Fig. 3. Block diagram showing the dump load for a little HPP.

d) Frequency Balance and Control

A power system is made up of several linked generators that can supply massive loads much like a single generator, but all the generators and consumers add to the system when demand fluctuates. Practically speaking, the electricity system is never in a state of balance because consumer demand is constantly fluctuating.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

MHPPs commonly employ mechanical hydraulic governors, electro-hydraulic PI governors, and electro-hydraulic PID governors to regulate load frequency. This study examines the use of an electro-hydraulic PID governor in the load frequency control technique. To demonstrate its advantages, the response of the suggested governor is compared with that of the mechanical hydraulic governor under various load fluctuations. The test system and its different components are modeled in PSCAD/EMTDC software.

A. Test System for Load Frequency Control

To analyze the proposed Load Frequency Control (LFC) system, which includes a DG system with two MHPPs operating in parallel, the test system is simulated using PSCAD software. Each DG unit has the capability to transmit a maximum power of 1.8 MW when operating at its full capacity of 2 MVA. The distribution system consists of 20 lumped loads and 26 buses and it is completely separate from the main grid. Figure 4 illustrates the distribution network, while Figure 5 showcases the distribution system model developed with the PSCAD/EMTDC software. The distribution line is modelled as a theoretical PI circuit with a maximum length of 6 km.

Fig. 4. MHPP connected with the distribution network.

B. Synchronous Generator Parameters

The two synchronous generator units in this research have nominal terminal voltages of 3.3 kV. Every generator has a transformer connected to it that steps up the voltage to 11 kV for the distribution network. The generators are linked to two circuit breakers. The synchronous generator model, equipped with a mechanical hydraulic governor and an electro-hydraulic PID-based governor, is designed with the PSCAD/EMTDC software. A hydraulic turbine that has every valve required to regulate the mechanical torque the water flow produces powers the generators. Another essential characteristic of the generators is excitement control, which is necessary because the device needs to maintain the voltage level within a specific range. The different synchronous generator parameters are shown in Table I. The transformer parameters corresponding to each generator are presented in Table II. Transformers are employed to convert the voltage level created by the generator from 3.3 KV to the distribution voltage level, which is 11 KV.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF A SYNCHRONOUS GENERATOR

Parameter	Value
Rated RMS line to line voltage	3.3 KV
Rated RMS line current	350 A
Inertia constant (H)	2.5 s
Iron loss resistance	300 p.u.
Base angular frequency	314.159 rad/s
Armature resistance [Ra]	0.01 p.u.
Potier reactance [Xp]	0.104 p.u.
Unsaturated reactance [XD]	0.838 p.u.
Unsaturated transient reactance [XD']	0.239 p.u.
Unsaturated transient time [TDo']	8.0 s
Unsaturated sub Transient time [TDo'']	0.05 s
Unsaturated reactance [Xq]	0.534 p.u.
Unsaturated sub transient reactance [Xq'']	0.12 p.u.
Unsaturated sub transient time [Tqo'']	1.0 p.u.
Air gap factor	1.0

TABLE II. TRANSFORMER PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
3 phase transformer MVA	2 MVA
Primary winding type	Delta
Secondary winding type	Star
Positive sequence leakage reactance	0.08 p.u.
Air core reactance	0.2 p.u.
Inrush decay time constant	1 s
Knee voltage	1.15 p.u.
Magnetizing current	0.001%

C. Exciter System Model

Giving the synchronous machine field winding direct current is the excitation system's primary job. Furthermore, the excitation system carries out control tasks that are necessary for the power system to operate satisfactorily. Voltage and reactive power flow control are examples of control functions. The excitation system autonomously regulates the field current of the synchronous generator in order to uphold the terminal voltage. The excitation system model chosen for this study is based on the IEEE type AC1A standard model shown in Figure 5. This model can be used with brushless excitation systems and offers a field-controlled alternator excitation system with uncontrolled rectifiers. The voltage regulator draws power from a source that is unaffected by transients in the outside world and the exciter does not use self-excitation. Table III lists the typical parameters used in the simulation.

TABLE III. SAMPLE DATA OF IEEE AC1A EXCITATION MODEL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
T_C	0	K_F	0.03
T_B	0	T_F	1
K_A	400	T_E	0.8
T_A	0.02	K_E	1
V_{AMAX}	14.5	K_C	0.2
V_{AMIN}	-14.5	K_D	0.38
V_{RMAX}	6.03	V_{RMIN}	-5.43
$SE_{(VE1)}$	0.1	$SE_{(VE2)}$	0.03
V_{E1}	4.18	V_{E2}	3.14

D. Model of Governor and Hydraulic Turbine

The major role of the governor is to regulate the generator speed in order to ensure a consistent frequency. The mechanical torque and power delivered to the generator are determined by the governor in order to control the water flow by detecting variations in velocity and adjusting the turbine gate accordingly. The main block diagram, which incorporates the governor and hydraulic turbine is seen in Figure 6. The turbine governor has to act fast to shut the hydraulic valve and divert water flow right away to prevent the hydro turbine from over-speeding when load is removed from the system and demand drops.

E. Electro-hydraulic PID Governor Transfer Function

The transfer function of the hydro governor model, also known as a PID controller, with proportional, integral, and derivative gain is shown in Figure 7. By offering both a transient gain increase and a transient gain reduction, it produces a higher response. Particularly when islanded mode is engaged, the significant derivative gain could lead to increased oscillations and instability. The proportionate and integral gains are responsible for producing the intended transient droop and reset time. In Figure 7, TA represents the time constant of both the pilot valve and servomotor. TC refers to the gain of the gate servo while TD represents the time constant of the gate servomotor. RP exhibits a persistent sagging. The governor model consists of two crucial parameters: the maximum rate at which the gate may open and close. These data demonstrate the pace at which the gate opens or closes, with the hydraulic turbine having a slower response compared to the steam or gas turbine. The PID parameters are shown in Table IV.

Fig. 5. IEEE type AC1A excitation transfer function.

Fig. 6. Speed control with turbine and governor.

Fig. 7. Electro-hydraulic PID governor transfer function.

TABLE IV. VALUE OF GOVERNOR MODEL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
K_P	2	T_C	0.2
K_I	0.35	T_D	0.2
K_D	0.9	Max gate opening	0.16
T_A	0.05	Max gate opening	0.16
R_P	0.004	Dead band value	0
Max gate position	1.0	Min gate position	0

F. Hydro Turbine

Water is commonly regarded as an incompressible fluid and a rigid conduit. The turbine flow is initially quantified as (q) before being diminished by a deflector and relief valves. Penstock head loss coefficient F_p is defined as follows: G is the gate position. The water beginning time is T_w , and the turbine gain factor flow is A_T . T_w shows how long it takes a head to speed up the water in the penstock. With load, this time varies from 0.5 to 4.0 s. The hydraulic turbine's transfer function is depicted in Figure 8. The hydraulic turbine's block diagram specifications are displayed in Table V. Lastly, the turbine model regulates the necessary mechanical power for the generator.

Fig. 8. Hydro turbine transfer function.

TABLE V. VALUE OF HYDRO TURBINE PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
T_w	1.0	Initial output power	0.7
f_p	0.02	Initial operating head	1.0
0	0.5	Rated output power	1.0

G. Mechanical Hydraulic Governor

The traditional mechanical hydraulic governor is made up of both hydraulic and mechanical parts. For stable functioning, this governor makes use of persistent droop features. Permanent droop characteristics are employed to provide equitable load sharing between generating units. The water inertia causes hydroelectric turbines to react nonlinearly. A servomotor is an intricately engineered electric motor that rotates in direct response to an electronic command signal. As stated in [33], the transfer function of the relay valve and gate servomotor is:

$$\frac{g}{b} = \frac{Ks}{s(1 + sT_p)} \tag{1}$$

where K_S is the servo gain and T_p is the pilot valve /servomotor time constants. A dashpot transfer function is given by [17]:

$$\frac{d}{g} = R_t \frac{sT_R}{(1 + sT_R)} \tag{2}$$

where R_t represents the temporary decrease in value, while T_R represents the duration it takes for the temporary decrease to return to its original value. Figure 9 illustrates the diagrammatic portrayal of a mechanical hydraulic governor.

Fig. 9. Mechanical hydraulic governor.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The test system is designed to measure an electrohydraulic PID governor’s reaction and a mechanical hydraulic governor that supplies power to a distribution network at both peak load and base load capacity. The test system is modelled and simulated using PSCAD software. The MHPP concept, along with its distribution network, can be seen in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. MHPP model with distribution network.

A. Case Studies

In various scenarios, the power plant's base and peak load are used to test the governors' responsiveness. Table VI presents scenarios of increasing and decreasing load to see how the governors react significantly.

TABLE VI. CASE STUDIES

Case Study	Details
Case No. 1 (a)	5% load is suddenly added to the base load.
Case No. 1 (b)	5% load is suddenly subtracted from the base load.
Case No. 2 (a)	5% load is suddenly added to the peak load.
Case No. 2 (b)	5% load is suddenly subtracted from the peak load.
Case No. 3 (a)	10% load is suddenly added to the base load.
Case No. 3 (b)	10% load is suddenly subtracted from the base load.

1) Case No 1 (a)

The generators are running at their base load, or minimum load, when a 5% load is added. The frequency will decrease as the load increases. The perturbation was introduced at $t = 20$ s. The combined reaction of the mechanical hydraulic governor and the electro-hydraulic PID governor are shown in Figure 11.

Fig. 11. Governors response for 5% addition of load.

According to Figure 11, it takes 31 s for the frequency to restore to its original value. Additionally, the electro-hydraulic PID governor exhibits reduced undershoot compared to the mechanical hydraulic governor. The mechanical hydraulic governor requires 40 s to return to its initial position.

Therefore, in comparison to the mechanical hydraulic governor, the electro-hydraulic PID-based governor exhibits reduced undershoot and necessitates a shorter duration.

2) Case No 1 (b)

Figure 12 illustrates how frequency increases in response to the drop in load and eventually returns to its initial value, contingent on the performance of both governors. The governors require 38.92 and 20 s, respectively, to reach 50 Hz values. Thus, in comparison to an electrohydraulic PID governor, a mechanical hydraulic governor has once again exhibited a delayed reaction and a greater degree of overshooting.

Fig. 12. Governors response for 5% reduction of load.

3) Case No 2 (a)

Suddenly, a 5% load is added to the generators, which are already running at maximum capacity. This load applied the disturbance at $t = 20$ s. The frequency drops as the load increases. Figure 13 displays the combined reaction of the hydraulic mechanical governor and the electrical PID governor. The electro-hydraulic PID governor clearly demonstrates a reduced amount of undershoot compared to the mechanical hydraulic governor. It takes 20.68 s for the frequency to return to its initial 50 Hz value, whereas the mechanical hydraulic governor requires 57.76 s to reach its operating frequency at 49.80 Hz during peak load.

Fig. 13. Governors response for 5% addition of load.

4) Case No 2 (b)

The generators are running at their maximum load (peak load) when a 5% reduction in load occurs. The frequency rises as the load decreases. The perturbation was introduced at $t = 20$ s. Figure 17 displays the combined reaction of the electro-

hydraulic PID governor and the mechanical hydraulic governor. Figure 14 shows that the electro-hydraulic PID governor has less overshoot than the mechanical hydraulic governor and that it takes 20.34 s for the frequency to return to its initial value of 50 Hz. The system will run at 49.90 Hz after the mechanical hydraulic governor takes 58.70 s to attain a frequency lower than 50 Hz.

Fig. 14. Governors response for 5% reduction of load.

5) Case No 3 (a)

A 10% load is added to the generators while they are running at base load capacity. Frequency reduces as load increases. At $t = 20$ s, the disturbance was administered. Figure 15 illustrates the collective response of the electro-hydraulic PID governor and the mechanical hydraulic governor. According to Figure 15, the electro-hydraulic PID governor exhibits lower undershoot compared to the mechanical hydraulic governor. It takes 33.14 s for the frequency to revert back to its original value of 50 Hz, while it takes 54.83 s for the mechanical hydraulic governor to attain a frequency of 49.92 Hz.

Fig. 15. Governor's response for 10% addition of load.

6) Case No 3 (b)

Figure 16 displays the response of both electro-hydraulic and mechanical hydraulic PID governors at the base load for a 10% load reduction. The frequency rises with decreasing load and returns to its initial value after a certain amount of time, contingent on the performance of both governors. The mechanical hydraulic governor in Figure 16 has a slower response and a bigger overshoot compared to the electro-hydraulic PID governor. Both electrohydraulic and mechanical hydraulic PID governors require 42 and 28.51 s, respectively, to obtain 50 Hz values.

Fig. 16. Governor's response for 10% reduction of load.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This research introduces an electro-hydraulic PID-based governor for regulating frequency and speed in a Micro-Hydro Power Plant (MHPP) in a distribution network. The governor implementation is conducted using the PSCAD/EMTDC software. The efficacy of load frequency management when employing an electro-hydraulic PID-based governor has been verified on a 26-bus test system under several load fluctuation scenarios at both peak and base capacities. The efficacy and resilience of the suggested electro-hydraulic PID-based governor have been examined in relation to load increments and decrements ranging from 5% to 10% at both minimum and maximum capacities. The performance of the electro-hydraulic PID-based governor was compared to that of the mechanical hydraulic governor. The simulation findings indicate that the mechanical hydraulic governor exhibits significant frequency overshoot and undershoot and requires a longer time to settle the frequency compared to the suggested electro-hydraulic PID-based governor. It has been confirmed that the suggested electro-hydraulic PID-based governor is effective and dependable in ensuring the safe and stable functioning of power systems, surpassing the current UFLS schemes. In future work, a more complex and hybrid-renewable energy system along with batteries can be integrated into the power system to enhance its flexibility and stability.

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Damage to Natural Gas Distribution Steel Pipelines caused by Rigid Bodies resulting from the Excavation of Laying Trenches

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ABSTRACT

The present paper focuses on analyzing the occurrence of defects such as dents and local deformations by laboratory simulations of a real case of a defect detected on a natural gas distribution pipeline laid at a depth of approximately 0.6 m. The defect is caused by a river stone which due to the compression forces, damages the pipe to the point of cracking. In the laboratory, the simulation was carried out on a steel pipe insulated with extruded polyethylene which was acted upon by a mandrel made of duralumin. The purpose of the tests is to determine the maximum values at which the pipe material fractures. It was found that the fracture of the pipes when there are rigid bodies in the protective layer of sand is accelerated by the sand existing between them and the pipe and by the change in the properties of the steel the pipes are made of when they are kept in water.

Keywords-pipelines; natural gas distribution; forces; fracture

I. INTRODUCTION

Distribution pipes are usually installed underground at a depth at least equal to the local frost depth. If we consider dividing the territory of Romania into areas according to the frost depth (STAS 6057-77), the frost depth in the Municipality of Sibiu where the research was conducted ranges between 900 and 1000 mm [1]. The underground distribution pipes are made of steel or high-density polyethylene [2]. The distribution pipeline routes are, as far as possible, straight, going along streets or thoroughfares. It is not allowed to install pipes under or along tram lines, railways, or channels that communicate with neighbouring buildings without special preparation. It is prohibited to pass the distribution pipelines under buildings or through their annexes [3].

The surface of the pipelines intended for the distribution of natural gas and its equipment can show a series of defects and imperfections, which affect the operational safety. The residual mechanical strength and the operational safety of the gas distribution pipelines are essentially influenced by the presence of defects. In this sense, this paper analyzes how the natural gas

distribution pipelines made of steel and insulated with extruded polyethylene can be damaged by the existence of rigid bodies resulting from the route excavation and unintentional contact with the surface of the pipes, especially on their upper side, where we consider the exerted mechanical force to be the greatest. These defects can be considered imperfections or geometric defects and represent deviations in size and shape that significantly change the configuration of the pipe's cross-section, leading up to the fracture of the material: dents and local deformations are traces of impacts or interaction with external forces [4, 5]. In this study, we simulate a real case identified on the distribution pipes located in our region which created malfunction in exploitation for the gas provider (Figure 1).

II. TEST PREPARATION

Starting from the defect shown in Figure 1 detected on the distribution network of pipelines in the Municipality of Sibiu, which occurred due to the existence of a river stone on the upper surface of the pipe, most likely resulting from the excavation of the laying trench and the inadequate depth of the

pipe network of approximately 0.6 m, we tried as much as possible to simulate this phenomenon in the laboratory. Thus, we processed a mandrel model to simulate the river stone, more precisely rounded at the end and with approximately the same dimensions as the defect, having an end in the form of a hemisphere with a radius of approximately 10 mm. The local printing by compression was carried out by this special mandrel made of hard aluminum (Figure 2), so that it had the necessary hardness to apply the forces in the order of 10^4 N [6].

Fig. 1. Defects as local deformations detected on the pipelines.

Fig. 2. Mandrel made of hard aluminium.

For the experiment, we substituted the section of the pipe where the defect was detected with L245 steel pipe segments, having \varnothing 60.3 mm diameter and 3.6 mm wall thickness, insulated with class B PEHD high-density polyethylene, with an applied thickness of 1.8 mm. The tests were carried out on three sets of pipes with a length of 600 mm: one set was kept in its original state, the second was kept in rainwater for 72 hr, and the third was kept in loam sand for 72 hr (Figure 3).

The compression tests were executed in a specialized laboratory equipped with the necessary tools for conducting physical-mechanical tests and analysis and non-distinctive checks (Figure 4), compliant with the European standards [7].

III. TEST EXECUTION

The forces resulting from the compression applied on the upper surface of the pipe section [8] are determined by using the assembly shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 3. Specimens of insulated pipe: (a) kept in water (b) or loam sand (c) for 72 hr.

Fig. 4. Compression testing machine.

IV. TEST RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

As can be seen, the pipe was subjected to different compressive forces from the testing machine, thus determining the maximum values in the moment of fracture (Figure 6) of the pipe material under the influence of compressive forces [8, 9]. The obtained data are shown in Table I. Regarding these data, it should be taken into account that it is impossible to keep the machine under constant load for more than 2 min and for this reason, the compression time at maximum force value was set at 2 min maximum, enough to read the compression values at the time of the pipe fracture [10, 11].

TABLE I. FRACTURE STRENGTH DEPENDING ON THE ENVIRONMENT.

Pipe material versus storage environment	Rupture strength [N]
Steel pipe pre-insulated with extruded polyethylene	66881
Steel pipe pre-insulated with extruded polyethylene and kept in sand for 72 hr	64723
Steel pipe pre-insulated with extruded polyethylene and kept in water for 72 hr	63743

Fig. 5. Detail of the assembly used for determining the fracture strength: (1) hard aluminium mandrel, (2) steel pipe by type L245, (3) special support to fix the pipe.

Fig. 6. Fracture of the pipe material.

V. OBSERVATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Analyzing the shown graphs and making a comparison between the different environments of the natural gas distribution networks, we conclude that the rupture strength of the pipe material is superior when the pipelines are kept in the atmospheric environment and decreases significantly when the samples are kept in sand or water. We consider that, in the case of pipes kept in sand, this is due to its granulation and hardness, and when they are kept in water, it is because water changes the properties of the steel the pipe is made of.

We can thus conclude that the fracture of the pipes in the situation when there are rigid bodies in the protective layer of sand is accelerated by the sand existing between them and the pipe and by the change in the properties of the steel the pipes are made of, when they are kept in water (see Figure 7). The next step in our study will be to analyze and simulate this case using the finite element method to determinate the behavior of the pipe subjected to similar loads.

Fig. 7. Rupture strength of the pipe depending on the environment.

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A Simulation Method for the One-time Snap-fit Assembly Process of PA6 GF60 - Components

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ABSTRACT

This paper's scope is to develop an intelligible Finite Element Analysis (FEA) method, utilized to determine and quantify the assembly forces required to assemble the snap-fit component, which is made of a glass fiber reinforced polyamide (type 6, 60% glass fiber, PA6 GF50), as well as to determine the snap-fit joint maximum retention forces. The proposed FEA method is to be used in Abaqus as a standard solver type, considering its operation ease and simplicity in creating the model. The setback of implementing the standard solver approach is that during the snap-fit assembly, at a certain point in the simulation, the behavior is transformed from a static movement to a dynamic one, precisely when the snap moves backward in the assembled position, at this point, due to the dynamic behavior of the simulation, the solution will continue to diverge, and the convergence is not achieved.

Keywords-snap-fit; standard solver; abaqus; polyamide; glass fiber reinforced

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is in a continuous development regarding the reduction of the cost [1], the component weight [2], the time spent on the production line, and the complexity of the assembled components, leading to a decrease in the exhaust emissions of internal combustion engine cars [3]. To achieve this, car manufacturers and the automotive suppliers of the components played a crucial role. Additionally, the quantity of the metal and metal alloys [4] used was reduced and replaced with innovative plastics, [5] such as polyamides reinforced with glass fiber. Finally, instead of assembling the components via screws to the snap-fit clips, components made of reinforced glass fiber polyamides were developed. The snap-fit [6] clip assembly process offers the possibility of streamlining the industrial assembly procedures in which the automotive industry is heavily involved. The reason is that the former method has several advantages, namely assembly or disassembly speed, and construction simplicity, due to which automation can be quickly and easily realized [7]. As far as snap-fit assemblies are concerned, the more recent literature does not offer an extensive range of different outlooks on them. However, an important part of the researchers' concerns is related to resolving some dimensional limitations of parts made

by engaging Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology as well as settling design issues. In the case of making parts larger than the workspace of 3D printers, researchers propose a solution whereby that part is divided into smaller ones and accumulated by these types of cheap and fast assemblies [8-10]. Also, in the context of quick-release assemblies in AM, authors in [11] conducted an experimental study on the determination of the required mating/dismounting force as a function of several predefined parameters. The experimental data were processed and compared with an analytical model expressed by a derived equation. Another perspective pinpointed in the literature is related to the identification of efficient robotic assembly methods using snap-fit elements. Unlike an assembly performed by a human operator, who validates it following an acoustic signal produced when the two parts have been collected, this is a challenge in robotic assembly. To meet this challenge, authors in [12] proposed a machine-learning method based on data obtained from force variation during the assembly process. Authors in [13] investigated the aspects of preload and stiffness factors as a technique of determining a complete and correct collection of snap-fit assemblies with seals or elastic gaskets where pre-tensioning is required. An even higher holding force and a higher engagement signal were found to lead to an increase in assembly confidence.

II. MATERIAL SELECTION

To be able to develop a simulation method that will provide results as close to reality as possible/credible results, a need for a good material definition has emerged. The input data for the material are chosen from [14]. Moreover, the same type of polyamide as the real component with the same amount of reinforcement material, in this case glass fiber, is selected. The material curve chosen from CAMPUS is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Raw data input for the material definition in Abaqus.

The stress–strain curve out of campus is evaluated as engineering stress–strain. To be used in the FEA [15, 16], it is required to be transformed into true form [17]. For this reason, the equations shown below are performed to obtain the input data for the FEA analysis.

$$\frac{F}{s} = \sigma \tag{1}$$

$$\ln \frac{l}{l_0} = \epsilon \tag{2}$$

$$\frac{F}{s_0} = \sigma_{eng} \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{l-l_0}{l_0} = \epsilon_{eng} \tag{4}$$

where F is the tensile force, s is the instantaneous section area, s_0 is the initial section area, l is the instantaneous length of the specimen, and l_0 is the initial length of the specimen.

The final material curve [18] that will be used in the FEA is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. True stress–strain curve for PA6 GF60.

III. SIMULATION METHOD

The simulation software utilized for determining the assembly forces as well as the maximum retention [19] force is Abaqus [20]. The simulation is formed employing two components: the snap-fit, as a deformable component and the body used as an analytical rigid component [21]. Nevertheless, in real life, the most substantial deformations occur only on the snap and no significant ones take place on the counterpart, while material data are considered for a non-linear simulation [22]. In Figure 3, the assembly is demonstrated. For a better solution convergence, the parts are arranged in direct contact [23], while no gap is preferred. The simulation is divided into 3 steps, shown in Figure 4. Regarding the boundary conditions, the snap is considered fixed in the bottom side whereas the body is free to move along the vertical axes. This is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 3. 3D models of components prepared for the FEA: (a) Snap, (b) body.

Name	Procedure	Nlgeom	Time
Initial	(Initial)	N/A	N/A
mount	Static, General	ON	1
step_back	Static, General	ON	1
unmount	Static, General	ON	1

Fig. 4. Simulation steps.

Fig. 5. Boundary conditions.

The main challenge for this type of simulation is to allow the snap to spring back into the assembled position while still using the Abaqus standard solver, while the resultant of the forces should be 0 throughout the steps. During the spring back into the final state moment, there is an instant force drop. So,

the solution goes from static to dynamic and the equilibrium equation of the standard solver will start to diverge. One quick solution is to use the Abaqus Explicit [24] solver, but in this case, the approach is not to be followed due to the simulation complexity. To prevent this, the total snap travel, up to the point where it is fixed to the axial travel end, is split in half: in the first half the snap is radially deformed until the middle of the body height. In this way, it is ensured that the maximum assembly force is reached, considering the surface quality of the reinforced plastic components, that the resulting friction between the parts is low, and that the given force can be neglected. The second half, however, is formed when the contact between the snap and body is removed while keeping the displacement imposed. By removing the contact, the resulting force of the complete movement is 0. A detailed view of how this interaction is composed is demonstrated in Figure 6. In the final step, the direction of the body displacement is reversed in order to quantify the maximum retaining force of the snap. In this step, the contact between the body and the lower flat surface of the snap is defined, as spotted in Figure 7.

Interaction Manager

Name	Initial	mount	step_back	unmount
body-snap-assembly	Created	Propagated	Deactivated	
body-snap-disassembly				Created

Fig. 6. Simulation interaction based on simulation steps.

Fig. 7. Displacement boundary condition formulation.

IV. TEST METHOD

The test entails using a snap-fit of an automotive component onto the chassis, as it is observed in Figure 8. Considering that the chassis is too big to fit onto a small test rig, a similar fixture is built while retaining the geometry conditions close to reality, as shown in the test setup in Figure 9. The test is conducted using an Instron 5544 in displacement, which is controlled by employing an imposed displacement of 10 mm/min. The body is moved downwards until the snap is fully seated (the force drops to 0 N). For the maximum retention force, the body is moved upwards until the snap is not assembled, it is either sheared or slips out of the assembly.

V. SIMULATION – TEST COMPARISON

Based on the simulation, two forces are calculated by plotting the field output, the reaction force and displacement of the body reference point. For the first two steps, the output is the maximum assembly force of the snap. A direct comparison between simulation and test is presented in Figure 10.

Fig. 8. Test component – snap fixture.

Fig. 9. Test Setup, (e) snap, (f) body.

Fig. 10. Maximum assembly force. Green: test, red: simulation.

For the third step, the output is directly correlated with the results derived from the test. The displacement where the snap

shearing occurs in the test is considered to be the critical part of the simulation point, when evaluating the maximum retention force of the snap-fit and is identified in Figure 11. The critical stress value from the FEA is compared and evaluated for the maximum radial displacement and the simulation results are shown in Figure 12.

Fig. 11. Maximum retention force. Green: test, red: simulation.

Fig. 12. Critical assembly stress value.

The critical stress value is evaluated for the limit where the material slope goes horizontal and thus the material starts to stretch. The stress in the corner of Figure 13, namely those above the imposed limit, are compressive stresses, and in this specific case, are not considered dangerous while evaluating the snap during the mounting step. For the dismantling step, a direct comparison of the snap stresses is made at the point where the shear of the snap occurs in reality. The results of the disassembly phase simulation in Abaqus can be seen in Figure 14. For the assessment of real situations [25], Figure 15 depicts the failure mode comparison in the test (a) and provides a detailed view of the critical area from the simulation (b).

Fig. 13. Stress in assembled position.

Fig. 14. Critical stress level for dismantling step.

Fig. 15. (a) Failure mode in test, (b) detailed view in the simulation.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

In the present work, the behavior of snap-fit assemblies was analyzed through numerical methods using numerical simulation tools. This analysis was carried out in order to reach a better understanding of the dynamic behavior of snap-fit assemblies, which is in line with the current concerns of the scientific community. Through the performed numerical simulations and the introduction of an intermediate step during the assembly simulation, after reaching the maximum radial displacement of the snap (maximum assembly force), the contact between the snap and the counterpart (the body) helps keeping the Abaqus standard as a solver. At the same time, this contact increases confidence for future results while the assembly force can be quantified. If needed, the parts can be optimized so that the assembly force is eliminated, reducing the cost and time invested into the assembly tools.

Future developments are required to establish a better evaluation of the critical point in the simulation when we can predict the snap out or the shearing of the plastic snaps. The next steps to follow concern the acquisition of ISO527 [26] tensile dog bone [27] samples, with fiber orientation distributed either along the tensile direction or perpendicularly to it, ideally built from the same supplier of the real component. Furthermore, stress estimation is expected to be obtained. The latter refers to strain data derived by applying a tensile test on them. With the resulting stress-strain data, the same method of obtaining the true form [17], employed in the FEA, can be used. In addition, a critical failure point can be chosen based on the tensile results. In this case, the test data are not necessary to establish the critical point.

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Radial Displacements in a Rotating Disc of Uniform Thickness Made of Functionally Graded Material

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ABSTRACT

The finite element method is used to calculate a rotating disc, which has a uniform thickness and is made of functionally graded materials, based on the concepts of multilayer disc and equivalent material. These concepts are also available for analytical calculus. The multilayered disc concept perceives the disc as constructed from several layers, and the equivalent material concept regards the disc material as composed of homogeneous and isotropic material but with fictitious properties equivalent in behavior to the functionally graded material. These two concepts, encompassed in this study, allow us to contemplate the variation according to the material law and Poisson's ratio, which is often neglected, to reduce the mathematical complexity. The concepts, models, and methods involved in this study were validated by employing numerical and analytical calculations. The proposed method introduced simplicity, precision, and accessibility to solve the complex problem of functionally graded structures. The calculus development, model validation, and result analysis were based on numerical calculus using the finite element method. The utilized models were grounded on the existence of an axial-symmetric plane. So, 2D or 3D simplified models can be used with several variants regarding the mesh fineness. This study results and models are useful to specialists and structure designers of this type, have a high degree of generality, and present opportunities for the application of other calculation methods.

Keywords-functionally graded material; equivalent material model; multi-layer wall; rotating disc; FEM

I. INTRODUCTION

The appearance and continuous development of Functionally Graded Materials (FGMs) have become a subject of scientific research based on at least two important aspects: their manufacture and their calculation. FGMs are very important to engineers, designers, and manufacturers because of their specific properties. They are considered composite materials [1-2], but they are considered as new materials [3]. This study investigates the problem of calculating structures from FGMs, focusing on the calculus of a rotating disc having a uniform thickness made of FGM. This study aimed to develop methods and models as accessible and efficient as possible to successfully solve calculus problems of structures made of FGMs. Analytical calculation of structures from FGMs raises mathematical difficulties in general [1, 4], which arise from the fact that engineers no longer work with material constants but with functions that describe the material properties.

Many material property laws exist. The problem becomes more complicated when considering this aspect for all properties [5-6]. For example, the Poisson ratio variation is often neglected, but the difficulties do not completely disappear [5-7]. This study introduces two concepts for approaching the calculation of FGM structures with an acceptable accuracy [8-10]: the multilayer structure concept and the concept of equivalent material (structure). This paper displays the calculus results of a rotating disc having a uniform thickness and made of FGMs using these two concepts. In addition, a comparative quantitative study on the influence of considering the Poisson ratio variation is exhibited [11]. The novelty of this study comprises a new approach development, based on the two original concepts, providing a method and practical calculation models for a widely used structure made of FGM. The proposed approach allows for viewing the Poisson ratio variation according to the adopted material law. To simplify the mathematical calculation, the variation of the Poisson ratio in the calculation of functionally graded structures was neglected.

II. FUNCTIONALLY GRADED DISC

FGMs represent a category of materials that can be called composites but whose elastic and physical properties along one of their dimensions, namely Young's modulus, shear modulus, density, Poisson ratio, thermal or electrical conductivity, etc., are described by material adopted laws (models) [1, 4, 8]. Usually, one of the materials is a high-resistance material (ceramic) and the other is a common material having low resistance, like aluminum, steel, etc. Such materials are increasingly being used in engineering design. Plates, beams, and tubes are perhaps the most commonly utilized structural elements of FGMs. Figure 1 shows a rotating disc that has a uniform thickness and is made of FGMs, where the highest material properties are on its outer contour and the lowest material properties are on the inner contour where the working pressure is also applied. Figure 2 presents a quarter of the rotating disc portrayed in Figure 1, built in the variation version on the thickness wall of the material properties.

Fig. 1. Thick-walled tube under internal pressure.

Fig. 2. Material property variation in FGMs.

The highest values are toward the outside (radius R_2) as the function $F(r)$ varies. There are many material property laws. The most used one is the power law [1, 4, 6, 8], which can be written as:

$$F(r) = F_b + (F_t - F_b) \left(\frac{r-R_1}{h}\right)^k \tag{1}$$

$$R_1 < r < R_2 \tag{2}$$

where $F(r)$ refers to any material property such as Young's modulus $E(r)$, Poisson ratio $\nu(r)$, density $\rho(r)$, etc., F_b is the

$F(r)$ value for $r = R_1$, F_t is the $F(r)$ value for $r = R_2$, h is the disc thickness, r is the coordinate that describes the position of a point in the wall material, h is the wall thickness and k is a coefficient (power coefficient), which may have different values, less than or greater than 1. The indices b and t refer to the extreme edges of the material: b for the lower face ($r=R_1$) and t for the upper face ($r=R_2$).

The power coefficient k influence is very important [8], as can be seen in Figures 3 and 4. The qualitative evolution of the relative values of Young's modulus $E(r)$ and Poisson's ratio $\nu(r)$ versus the value of the relative radius and the power coefficient k can be followed by examining Figures 3 and 4. The evolution curves of the density are similar to the curves for $E(r)$. The calculation of structures from FGMs raises a series of difficulties, caused by the variation of material properties, even if the variation occurs according to a known law [12-14]. To overcome certain challenges, this study introduced two calculus concepts disclosed in the following case study.

Fig. 3. Relative Young's modulus versus r and k .

Fig. 4. Relative Poisson's ratio versus r and k .

III. CASE STUDY

This study examines a rotating disc of uniform thickness, made of FGM with an inner radius $R_1 = 0.005$ m and $R_2 = 0.005$ m, without any applied pressure, but with a rotation of 628 rad/s ($n = 6000$ rot/min). The disc was constructed from an FGM based on two materials having the properties showcased in Table I.

TABLE I. MATERIAL PROPERTIES

Materials:	Ceramic	Aluminum
Position	Top	Bottom
$E [Pa]$	3.8E+11	7.0E+10
$\nu [-]$	0.22	0.33
$P [kg/m^3]$	3960	2700

The material law is the power law represented by (1). The solution of the case study consists of the calculus of the disc wall radial displacements. The objective is achieved using three models with finite elements in five discretization variants to highlight the influence of the number of layers of the considered model. This study also accentuates the impact of contemplating the variation of Poisson's ratio or adopting different constant values.

IV. THE MULTILAYER WALL CONCEPT

The calculus of the rotating disc, having a uniform thickness, and made of FGMs, using the concept of multilayer wall, regards the disc wall reconstructed from overlapping layers of material, each layer having constant material properties (as a homogeneous and isotropic material), as shown in Figure 5. The property values of each layer are calculated based on the material law of FGM, for an average value of the coordinate corresponding to the middle of each layer [9-10]. Therefore, the continuous variation of the material properties is replaced by a variation in steps, defined by the respective layers. A greater number of considered layers leads to a closer solution to reality [10].

Fig. 5. Multilayer tube wall.

Choosing the layer number is an important issue to which this study gives useful answers. Using the multilayer wall concept for the thick-walled tube, 5, 10, 20, 30, and 40 layers were successively adopted. For each layer, a constant value of the material characteristics was calculated, applying the material power law according to (1), where the coordinate r is the average value of the r coordinates that describe the separation lines of the respective layer ($r_j^{av} \equiv r_{layer}^{av}$, as shown in Figure 6 and Table II). Table II displays the values of Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio for the case of 20 layers and $k = 0.05$.

TABLE II. YOUNG'S MODULUS, POISSON RATIO, AND DENSITY VALUES FOR EACH LAYER, FOR $k = 0.05$

Layer No.	Average radius r_{layer}^{av} [m]	Young's modulus $E(r)$ [Pa]	Poisson ratio $\nu(r)$ [-]	Density $\rho(r)$ [kg/m ³]
-	-	[Pa]	[-]	[kg/m ³]
1	0.0051	3.278E+11	0.239	3747.8
2	0.0053	3.423 E+11	0.233	3806.9
3	0.0055	3.494 E+11	0.231	3835.6
4	0.0057	3.541 E+11	0.229	3854.8
5	0.0059	3.577 E+11	0.228	3869.4
6	0.0061	3.606 E+11	0.227	3881.2
7	0.0063	3.631 E+11	0.226	3891.1
8	0.0065	3.652 E+11	0.225	3899.7
9	0.0067	3.670 E+11	0.225	3907.2
10	0.0069	3.687 E+11	0.224	3914.0
11	0.0071	3.702 E+11	0.224	3920.1
12	0.0073	3.715 E+11	0.223	3925.6
13	0.0075	3.728 E+11	0.223	3930.7
14	0.0077	3.740 E+11	0.222	3935.5
15	0.0079	3.751 E+11	0.222	3939.9
16	0.0081	3.761 E+11	0.222	3944.0
17	0.0083	3.770 E+11	0.221	3947.9
18	0.0085	3.779 E+11	0.221	3951.6
19	0.0087	3.788 E+11	0.221	3955.1
20	0.0089	3.796 E+11	0.221	3958.4
Average values:		3.654 E+11	0.225	3900.8

The curves in Figures 6 and 7, constructed with the values in Table II, comparatively illustrate the multilayer disc wall concept. The evolution in steps in the rotating disc thickness is compared to the continuous evolution. For both properties, in the inner surface proximity, the steps are large and then they decrease, being close to the continuous curve. This aspect is explained by the very different properties of these two materials and the very low power coefficient. Its increase leads to flattening of the curve and even the change of the curvature center. The large variation between steps moves to the other extreme surface, with the increase in the power coefficient value. It can be observed that the power coefficient k influence is very important.

Fig. 6. Young's modulus step variation.

V. THE EQUIVALENT MATERIAL CONCEPT

The equivalent material concept applies to the given structure without any modification of its geometry and

dimensions and consists of replacing the FGM with a homogeneous and isotropic material with equivalent properties. These properties are determined as the average of the calculated values, based on the material law and a number of lines or layers, as shown in Figure 6. Using the concept of equivalent material for a disc with uniform thickness means replacing the real properties with fictitious ones for a homogeneous and isotropic material with the same geometry. It was found that the equivalent value (equivalent material concept) of the entire FGM was the arithmetic mean of the values considered for each layer or line. Table III presents the equivalent Young's modulus for different values of the power coefficient as well as 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 80 layers.

Fig. 7. Poisson's ratio step variation.

TABLE III. EQUIVALENT YOUNG'S MODULUS OF FGM

k	Young's Modulus [Pa]x10 ¹¹					
	Layer number					
	5	10	20	30	40	80
0.05	3.661	3.657	3.654	3.654	3.653	3.653
0.10	3.532	3.521	3.521	3.521	3.521	3.519
0.25	3.110	3.184	3.184	3.184	3.184	3.181
0.50	2.781	2.769	2.769	2.769	2.769	2.767
1.00	2.250	2.250	2.250	2.250	2.250	2.250
2.00	1.723	1.733	1.733	1.733	1.733	1.733
4.00	1.299	1.319	1.319	1.319	1.319	1.320
6.00	1.113	1.141	1.141	1.141	1.141	1.143
8.00	1.005	1.042	1.042	1.042	1.042	1.044

The function of this equivalent module varies with the power coefficient and the number of layers. An important problem that arises when using the multilayer wall concept is the choice of the number of layers. As it is not possible to work with an infinite number, a reasonable number must be chosen [15-16], which ensures the required accuracy of the calculus of functionally graded discs. The equivalent modulus of elasticity (Young's modulus) is slightly influenced by the number of layers but strongly determined by the power coefficient *k*. The results of the investigation of the number of layers were published in [16-17], but we also have an available recommendation regarding the layer thickness in (3). Such a value allowed us to obtain acceptable results.

$$th_L \leq h/20 [m] \tag{3}$$

TABLE IV. EQUIVALENT POISSON RATIO OF FGM

k	ν _{ech} [-]					
	Layer number					
	5	10	20	30	40	80
0.05	0.225	0.225	0.225	0.225	0.225	0.225
0.10	0.229	0.230	0.230	0.230	0.230	0.230
0.25	0.241	0.242	0.242	0.242	0.242	0.242
0.50	0.256	0.256	0.257	0.257	0.257	0.257
1.00	0.275	0.275	0.275	0.275	0.275	0.275
2.00	0.294	0.293	0.293	0.293	0.293	0.293
4.00	0.309	0.308	0.308	0.308	0.308	0.308
6.00	0.315	0.315	0.314	0.314	0.314	0.314
8.00	0.319	0.318	0.318	0.318	0.318	0.318

The two concepts utilized, the multilayer wall and the equivalent material, demonstrate the great advantage of either considering the variation of Poisson's ratio or not, in addition to accessibility. Poisson's ratio variation is performed according to the same procedure and methodology presented for Young's modulus, and its equivalent values are depicted in Table IV. The analysis of the data in Table IV shows that the Poisson ratio variation with the number of layers is practically negligible. An important variation exists concerning the power coefficient. The equivalent density can be calculated by:

$$dM(r) = \rho(r) \cdot dV(r) \tag{4}$$

$$\rho(r) = \rho_b + (\rho_t - \rho_b) \left(\frac{r-R_1}{h}\right)^k \tag{5}$$

$$dM = 2\pi\rho_b r dr + 2\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_b)}{h^k} (r - R_1)^k r dr \tag{6}$$

$$M = 2\pi\rho_b \int_{R_1}^{R_2} r dr + 2\pi \frac{(\rho_t - \rho_b)}{h^k} \int_{R_1}^{R_2} (r - R_1)^k r dr \tag{7}$$

$$V = \pi(R_2^2 - R_1^2) \tag{8}$$

$$\rho_{echiv} = \frac{M}{V} \tag{9}$$

Using these equations and the data from the case study for the power law with coefficient *k* = 0.05, the equivalent density (ρ_{ech}) value is 3908.36 kg/m³. The equivalent density value, as an average of the values of each layer, is 3900.80 kg/m³ and this differs from the analytical calculus by -0.19%. The value of this error practically validates the proposed multilayer wall concept and gives confidence and safety to the calculation of the rotating disc, made of FGMs, using both concepts.

VI. ANALYTICAL CALCULUS OF FGDS USING EQUIVALENT PROPERTIES.

The analytical calculus follows the general theory of a rotating disc having a uniform thickness [18]. Engaging a polar reference system (*r*, θ) on the cross-section (the *z*-axis is the rotating disc axis), where the *r* direction coincides with the *x*-axis, the traditional notations from the elasticity theory, and the calculus model displayed in Figure 8. The differential equation of the radial displacements $u=u(r)$ is written as [18]:

$$\frac{d^2u}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{du}{dr} - \frac{u}{r^2} = -\frac{1-\nu^2}{E} \rho \omega^2 r \tag{10}$$

The solution of this equation is:

$$u(r) = \frac{\rho\omega^2}{8E} \left[\frac{(3+\nu)}{(1-\nu)} (R_1^2 + R_2^2)r + \frac{(3+\nu)}{(1-\nu)} \cdot \frac{R_1^2 R_2^2}{r} - (1 - \nu^2)r^3 \right] \quad (11)$$

In (11), ν can also be a ν_{ech} , an adopted constant value, or a function $\nu(r)$. Table V presents the analytical calculus results, based on an equivalent material concept [9, 16] and using equivalent values for a multilayer wall (20 layers). In (4) and (5), the density is considered constant at the value of the equivalent density. This can be evaluated as the average of density values at the level of lines or layers (Figure 6). Table V shows a relatively low influence of Poisson's ratio and a very good agreement of the results for $\nu = \nu(r)$ for its equivalent value of 0.225.

Fig. 8. The calculus model of the disk element equilibrium.

TABLE V. THE RESULTS OF THE ANALYTICAL CALCULUS FOR POWER COEFFICIENT $k = 0.05$

r [m]	$\nu = 0.30$	$\nu = 0.225$	$\nu(r)$
	u(r) [m]		
0.0050	1.525E-09	1.543E-09	1.535E-09
0.0052	1.506E-09	1.527E-09	1.524E-09
0.0054	1.489E-09	1.513E-09	1.511E-09
0.0056	1.474E-09	1.501E-09	1.499E-09
0.0058	1.461E-09	1.490E-09	1.489E-09
0.0060	1.449E-09	1.480E-09	1.479E-09
0.0062	1.438E-09	1.472E-09	1.471E-09
0.0064	1.428E-09	1.464E-09	1.464E-09
0.0066	1.419E-09	1.457E-09	1.457E-09
0.0068	1.41E-09	1.451E-09	1.451E-09
0.0070	1.401E-09	1.444E-09	1.445E-09
0.0072	1.394E-09	1.438E-09	1.439E-09
0.0074	1.386E-09	1.433E-09	1.434E-09
0.0076	1.378E-09	1.427E-09	1.429E-09
0.0078	1.371E-09	1.421E-09	1.423E-09
0.0080	1.363E-09	1.415E-09	1.418E-09
0.0082	1.355E-09	1.409E-09	1.412E-09
0.0084	1.347E-09	1.403E-09	1.406E-09
0.0086	1.339E-09	1.396E-09	1.400E-09
0.0088	1.33E-09	1.389E-09	1.393E-09
0.0090	1.321E-09	1.381E-09	1.385E-09

VII. MODELS WITH THE FINITE ELEMENTS OF FUNCTIONALLY GRADED DISCS

Three main finite element models were used. Figures 9 and 10 show the version with 20 material layers. In the performed calculations, these models were utilized in several variants, having 5, 10, 20, 30, and 40 layers. Each time, at least two

finite elements were employed for the thickness of one layer. The first finite element model, shown in Figure 9(a), is a 2D model, using PLANE182 element, in-plane stress/strain, from the finite element library of Ansys software. PLANE182 is a finite element with 4 nodes, two degrees of freedom per node, and linear interpolation functions [17, 19-21]. The second FE model, depicted in Figure 9(b), is also a 2D model utilizing the same PLANE182 element [22], but with its option as an axial-symmetric finite element. Figure 10 illustrates the finite element Model-3, which is a 3D one that uses the SOLID185 element. The finite element model is a brick type, with 8 nodes and three degrees of freedom per node [17, 23]. This model is a simplified one, based on the existence of two planes of symmetry [24-25]. The longitudinal dimension is an arbitrary one of 0.005 m.

Fig. 9. Finite element Model-1 and Model-2.

Fig. 10. Finite element Model-3.

VIII. RESULTS OF NUMERICAL CALCULUS BY FEM

The finite element models were organized for the analysis and presentation of the results as follows:

- Model-1: 2D, plane stress, equivalent material
- Model-2: 2D, plane stress, 20 layers, equivalent material
- Model-3: 3D, brick 8 nodes, equivalent material
- Model-4: 2D, axi-symmetric, equivalent material

Table VI entails the findings of the finite element analysis for these four calculus models. Figure 11 illustrates the field of radial displacements in the rotating FGM disc. There is a very

good agreement between the models and a very good closeness to the analytically calculated values based on the equivalent material, especially when using the 2D model in the plane stress state. Model-1 and Model-3 showed errors below 1%.

rotating FGM disc and that of the finite element modeling. Between those four considered models, the radial displacement values are practically the same. Therefore, any of these four models can be applied in practice. Moreover, the results of the numerical calculus with FE are extremely close to those of the analytical calculus, based on the equivalent material concept. This calculus concept is easier to use and leads to closer findings to the ones of the analytical solution.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to provide methods and models for the calculus of rotating discs made of FGMs, which should be accessible, precise enough, and as operational as possible. Along with other structural elements, such as plates and beams, rotating discs are widely used, and their realization from FGMs can lead to special technical performances. The calculus of a rotating disc made of FGMs was based on the concepts of multilayer wall and equivalent material. Both calculus concepts can be employed in numerical analysis by the FE method. Any elastic or physical properties of the material can be implemented in the equivalent material (Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, density). The use of the multilayer material concept allows us to consider the simultaneous variation of all the material characteristics in the case of numerical calculus utilizing the finite element method. The theoretical concepts of approaching the calculus of the rotating disc made of FGMs were practically exemplified in a case study to make possible the substantiation of the conclusions and observations through quantitative arguments.

The material law considered in the case study was the power law, which is one of the most common laws involved in the manufacturing of FGMs. The power coefficient usual value is a factor that favors the imposition of superior properties of the functional component materials, but in all cases, a study was carried out regarding its influence on the results. Every time and in all the situations studied, the power factor impact was significant, which substantially determined the behavior of the rotating disc under load. The load taken into account in this paper was only the inertial force as a result of the disk rotation, although the same method can be used for internal and/or external pressure loading. The study considered the multilayer wall to have 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 80 layers. The accuracy of the results was fully consistent with the characteristics of the finite element method. The analytical calculus presented, based on the concept of equivalent material (homogeneous and isotropic material with equivalent characteristics), represents a valid way of solving similar problems.

Both analytical calculations based on the concept of equivalent material as well as the numerical calculation using the finite element method can acknowledge the simultaneous variation of the Poisson ratio on the wall thickness. This study findings confirm the statement that the influence of a variable Poisson ratio is small, but complete neglect in any situation is debatable. The use of such discs is varied and a high precision of the calculation is absolutely necessary, therefore, this may require contemplating the variation of the Poisson ratio. Neglecting the variation of Poisson's ratio mainly brings convenience to the mathematical calculation, but can sometimes lead to unwanted errors. Finally, a general

Fig. 11. Finite element models: (a) Model-1, (b) Model-2, (c) Model-3, and (d) Model-4.

TABLE VI. COMPARATIVE RESULTS

Results	w_{R_1} [m]*10 ⁻⁹			w_{R_2} [m]*10 ⁻⁹		
	Analyt.	FE	Err. [%]	Analyt.	FE	Err. [%]
Model-1	1.568	1.56	-0.51	1.358	1.37	0.73
Model-2		1.56	-0.64		1.37	0.73
Model-3		1.55	-1.27		1.26	-7.35
Model-4		1.56	-0.64		1.27	-6.62

TABLE VII. COMPARATIVE RESULTS

r [m]	$u(r)_{analytic}$ [m]	$u(r)_{FEM}$ [m]	Errors [%]
0.0050	1.568E-09	1.560E-09	-0.51
0.0052	1.548E-09	1.538E-09	-0.70
0.0054	1.531E-09	1.522E-09	-0.59
0.0056	1.516E-09	1.509E-09	-0.49
0.0058	1.502E-09	1.496E-09	-0.38
0.0060	1.490E-09	1.486E-09	-0.28
0.0062	1.478E-09	1.476E-09	-0.19
0.0064	1.468E-09	1.467E-09	-0.10
0.0066	1.458E-09	1.458E-09	-0.01
0.0068	1.449E-09	1.451E-09	0.07
0.0070	1.441E-09	1.443E-09	0.16
0.0072	1.433E-09	1.436E-09	0.23
0.0074	1.425E-09	1.429E-09	0.31
0.0076	1.417E-09	1.422E-09	0.37

Table VII compares the outcomes of the analytical calculation with those of the numerical one utilizing Model-1. The comparative analysis of the numerical results practically validates the two calculus concepts (multilayer wall and equivalent material). From the data in Tables VI and VII, a series of useful conclusions arise, both for the analysis of the

conclusion regarding this study can be that the methods and models presented are operational, accessible, can be supported by usual structural analysis programs through the finite element method, and have a high degree of generality.

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Seagull Optimization Algorithm with Share Creation with an Image Encryption Scheme for Secure Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks

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ABSTRACT

A Vehicular Ad hoc Network (VANET) allows transmission, amid moving or stationary vehicles via wireless technology. Amongst several problems, safe transmission is the most important one in smart VANETs in 5G networks. Smart vehicles require integration with advanced road systems encompassing smart payment and traffic control systems. Numerous security mechanisms are used in VANETs to ensure safe communication. One such mechanism is cryptographic digital signatures based on encryption. This study introduces the new seagull optimization algorithm involving share creation with an image encryption scheme (SGOA-SCIES) for secure VANET transmissions. The goal of the SGOA-SCIES technique is to create a considerable number of shares and encrypt them to accomplish security. In the SGOA-SCIES technique, a Multiple Share Creation (MSC) scheme is employed to generate numerous share sets. For the share encryption process, the SGOA-SCIES technique engages the Fractional-Order Chaotic System (FOCS) approach to encrypt the generated shares. The optimal keys of the FOCS method can be chosen by the SGOA usage, which ameliorates the security level. The performance evaluation of the SGOA-SCIES method is examined on benchmark data. The simulations demonstrate the enhanced SGOA-SCIES methodology outcome and compare it with the ones of other existing systems and under the implementation of various measures.

Keywords-security; vehicular ad-hoc network; encryption; key generation; share creation

I. INTRODUCTION

VANETs are considered a developing concept that allows dependable, infotainment-rich, and safe driving networking [1]. However, service providers, automobile manufacturers, and governments are still hesitant to employ VANETs due to certain difficulties generated during their usage, namely user options, requirements for infrastructure, cost, security and safety problems [2]. In the past, the automotive industry concentrated on in-car technology for upgrading entertainment and navigation systems. However, currently the research community engaged special focus of their studies on VANETs due to the increased computation, processing, and computational capacity of the higher-end vehicles [3]. These capacities allowed the evolution of V2I (vehicle-to-infrastructure) and V2V (vehicle-to-vehicle) transmission [4].

These transmission models may provide customers with protection and infotainment applications instead of only offering them particular applications, like a challenged endpoint, which could for instance be a friend's home or a restaurant in another city [5].

Various safety challenges are considered for providing information security defence in vehicular networks, among which, access control and data privacy are highly significant [6]. Data confidentiality confirms that the former cannot be revealed or leaked to unauthorized vehicles or nodes. For providing data integrity and confidentiality in VANET communication, encryption is employed to enable only authenticated users to acquire the transmitted information [7]. Conventional symmetrical data encryption could be a result, yet it requires communication expenses for establishing

authentication keys among data recipients and senders that prominently decrease the time consumed for accessing the resources. An alternate intuitive solution is to encrypt every piece of information with the receiver vehicle's public key and indicate the data prior to their transmission [8]. Given that data are generally transferred to numerous vehicles, there are several data ciphertexts by these standard encryption methods that fail to achieve real-time conditions of data distribution in vehicular applications [9]. This problem can be tremendously severe on the environments of security application's accurate timing limits. Besides that, access control maintenance is a massively unresolved issue, especially, in cases where there is no centralized access control for disseminating the encrypted data in extremely dynamic surroundings [10].

II. RELATED WORKS

Authors in [11] developed the fully homomorphic encryption with the optimum key generation secure group communication (FHEOKG-SGC) system. Initially, this method presents an FHE-based encoding system and later the keys in the FHE technique are effectively selected via SCA. Simultaneously, the plum tree model can be exploited for detecting routes. In [12], a dual-channel encryption technique is designed. Firstly, a chaotic map controls the preliminary value of 5D conservative chaotic systems. Then, a chaotic sequence is exploited as convolution kernels of CNN for generating plaintext correlated chaotic pointers. An image fusion technique, which fuses and splits images into two parts, is proposed. Authors in [13] designed the EPO-based Routing Protocol (EPORP) for an outbreak detection in Sybil. The Sybil attack is discovered through the rumour riding method. The Split XOR (SXOR) operator is implemented for optimizing VANET safety. The optimum keys are carefully selected through the EPO technique. Authors in [14] developed an image encryption technique by joining chaotic maps and Josephus problems. The entire encryption procedure implements the traditional permutation–diffusion model. During permutation, the double-chaotic cycle technique is devised by upgrading the chaotic shift transformation technique. During diffusion, the Josephus problem description is prolonged through chaotic maps to retain the Josephus sequence diversity. In [15], a 7D hyperchaotic map produces the secret key for image encryption. A minimax DE model provides the ideal parameter for the hyperchaotic maps. The parameter fitness is assessed by the entropy and correlation coefficient. Then, the secret key is generated by the hyperchaotic maps. This key performs the diffusion process on the input image and produces an encrypted image. Authors in [16] put forward adaptive safety-aware lottery-EDF schedulers for constrained resources packet switching of Ethernet network with the GAIA multi-agent method. This scheme employs periodic, non-shared cryptographic key generation operations of varying sizes based on textual features in digital images stored on the server.

Authors in [17] introduced a chaotic cryptographic-based privacy safeguarding method to increase privacy in MANET-IoT. The key-generating operation in chaotic mapping can be enhanced by producing the optimum key pair via the recently established SA-SFO method. The key nominated from the

chaotic maps can be impacted by choosing the optimum parameter via SA-SFO. Authors in [18] propose BDIE-AOFOLS, a blockchain-based image encryption method utilizing an arithmetical optimization algorithm with a fractional-order Lorenz system, optimizing key generation for the highest PSNR values. In [19], an energy-efficient ROACM protocol is introduced for ad hoc wireless networks, incorporating path discovery, metric-based selection, and optimal bandwidth allocation via a seagull optimization algorithm. The summary covers various encryption methods, including fully homomorphic encryption, dual-channel encryption, adaptive lottery-EDF schedulers, blockchain-based image encryption, and the mentioned ROACM protocol.

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

In the presented study, the SGOA-SCIES method is suggested for the share encryption in VANETs, in an attempt to produce numerous shares and encrypt them for enhanced security. It comprises three operation stages: MSC, FOCS-based share encryption, and SGOA-based key generation. Figure 1 shows the workflow of the SGOA-SCIES system.

Fig. 1. Workflow of the SGOA-SCIES method.

A. Share Creation Procedure

Here, the MSC is enforced for producing a share collection. The RGB values are respectively determined in the matrix form

(R_m, G_m, B_m) and the extraction of actual image pixel value is conducted [20]. The matrix size is the same as the input image $(P * Q)$ and are described as:

$$\text{Pixel} = \sum R + G + B \quad (1)$$

Pixel depicts the overall amount of $R_m, G_m,$ and B_m values.

B. Share Creation

Each pixel that exists in the input images can be expressed by n transformed means, called shares. Each share includes sub-pixels of the RGB images. Based on the pixel value, the $R,$ $G,$ and B shares exist in the RGB images and are characterized as $R_s, G_s,$ and B_s as follows:

$$R_s = \int_1^k \lim_{k \rightarrow 1 \text{ ton}} R_{ab} \quad (2)$$

$$G_s = \int_1^k \lim_{k \rightarrow 1 \text{ ton}} G_{ab} \quad (3)$$

$$B_s = \int_1^k \lim_{k \rightarrow 1 \text{ ton}} B_{ab} \quad (4)$$

where a and b show the matrix location, $R_s, G_s,$ and B_s symbolize the share of RGB and $R_{ab}, G_{ab},$ and B_{ab} indicate the image pixel component. The pixel value of RGB is taken from the original images and retained as an individual matrix. Then, the share is created based on the splitting of images into different parts. The objective of SMSC is to encrypt the images into an amount of insignificant shared imaging. The shares do not define any valuable data if the share is collectively incorporated.

The elementary matrices should be derived before share creation, based on the amount of shares to be generated that are predefined by the user. The matrix is obtained if the outputs of RGB in the pixels are partitioned by S . In general, the block size is found to be 4×4 or 8×8 . Also, an arbitrary key is provided by the input imaging block size. The amount of share is described as 2^S if $S \geq 2$. Later, the shares are derived by carrying out the XOR operation of the basic matrix on different combinations. In such cases, the share and matrix counts are 4 and 2. By splitting the RGB values of the pixel by 2, the matrix is derived. For instance, assume the block is of size 2×2 , the RGB value is defined. Then, the key matrix K_M is arbitrarily produced. The basic matrix is formulated by the aforementioned process and is characterized by B_{M1} and B_{M2} correspondingly. Before share creation, the succeeding process is conducted with the XR_1 and XR_2 matrices.

$$XR_1 = 128 - B_{M1} \quad (5)$$

$$XR_2 = B_{M2} \quad (6)$$

The red band share is formed by XORing both matrices:

$$Rs1 = XR_1 \oplus K_M \quad (7)$$

$$Rs2 = XR_2 \oplus XR_1 \quad (8)$$

$$Rs3 = XR_2 \oplus Rs1 \quad (9)$$

$$Rs4 = Rs1 \oplus R \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{cases} s_1 = (x_t(300) \times 100 - \text{floor}(x_t(300) \times 100)) \times 10^6 \text{ mod } m \\ s_2 = (x_t(500) \times 100 - \text{floor}(x_t(500) \times 100)) \times 10^6 \text{ mod } m \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

The abovementioned process is reiterated for the remaining green and blue bands to produce various shares.

C. Share Reconstruction

Various shares are merged to form the actual images in the share reconstruction process.

$$R = Rs1 \oplus Rs2 \oplus Rs3 \oplus Rs4 \oplus K_M \quad (11)$$

$$G = Gs1 \oplus Gs2 \oplus Gs3 \oplus Gs4 \oplus K_M \quad (12)$$

$$B = Bs1 \oplus Bs2 \oplus Bs3 \oplus Bs4 \oplus K_M \quad (13)$$

Encryption and decryption by applying the FOCS technique are employed on every colour band when the share is reconstructed. Before the encryption and decryption processes, the colour band images are split into various blocks. The blocks are divided into the 4×4 dimension. Various shares are produced and the encryption technique is exploited. Then the FOCS-based encryption technique is exploited on the shares.

D. Share Encryption using the FOCS Technique

FOCS approach is used to encrypt the shares. A color image encryption model is introduced using FOCS by combining 3 chaotic models (Fractional Lorenz System (FLS), Tent Map (TM), and Arnold Map (AM)) [21]. At first, the color plain image was divided into $R, B,$ and G layers. Then, 3 layers are scrambled with AM, where the key and R and G layers are the initial value of the former, and other 2 are scrambling. The gray values of RGB are moulded and employed as an initial value of FLS. Then, add-mode diffusing is implemented. Lastly, the encrypted images are obtained. The pixel matrix size is $M \times M \times 3$, the plain images are signified as $A,$ and the encryption process can be defined as follows:

Step 1: Enter P plain images and K keys, and assume the size of A is $M \times M \times 3$. Read the primary values and parameters of AM in K and exploit AM to scramble the plain images. Select the last 2 pixels of R layers, attain the gray values as AM parameter while scrambling the G layer, and employ the function which is same as scrambling B layer to get image P_1 .

$$P_1 = \begin{Bmatrix} R \\ G \\ B \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} r(1), r(2), r(3), \dots, r(m) \\ g(1), g(2), g(3), \dots, g(m) \\ b(1), b(2), b(3), \dots, b(m) \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$m = \text{MIN} \quad (15)$$

Step 2: Read the initial values of TM $X(0)$ from key K . The TM is repeated 800 times. The first 300 conversion conditions are rejected and takes of the state values are represented as K_r .

$$K_\zeta = [x_t(200), x_t(300), x_t(400), x_t(500)] \quad (16)$$

Step3: Use (17) to make the K_ζ into s_1 and s_2 coordinates to place the pixels in P_1 . The FLS is repeated MIV and $2MN$ times, with smaller model perturbation repeated every 3000 times. This repetition occurs to attain the dimension of $3 \times MIV$ and $3 \times 2MIV$ of the new pseudo-random sequence S_1 and S_2 that are transformed (18) to password K_1 and K_2 .

$$K_o = \begin{bmatrix} K_{o1} \\ K_{o2} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R_{s1}, G_s, B_{s1} \\ R_{s2}, G_{s2}, B_{s2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{cases} K_1(j) = (\text{floor}(S_1(j) \times 2^{16}) \bmod 256) + 1 \\ K_2(j) = (\text{floor}(S_2(j) \times 2^{16}) \bmod 256) + 1 \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Step4: The password K_1 to transfer the information between the layers of images is used. It is calculated as:

$$\begin{cases} r'(i) = r(i) \oplus k_1(1,i) \oplus b(i) \\ g'(i) = g(i) \oplus k_1(2,i) \oplus r(i), i = 1,2, \dots, MIN \\ b'(i) = b(i) \oplus k_1(3,i) \oplus g'(i) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where $r'(i)$, $g'(i)$, and $b'(i)$ show the pixel value after diffusing. Then the pixel, which addresses to the plain data of each layer, is diffused into other 2 layers. This enhances the ability to resist the selected-plain attack.

E. Optimal Key Generation by Utilizing SGOA

At the final stage, the SGOA is applied to produce an optimal set of keys for the FOCS approach. The SGOA is based on the inspiration of the movement pattern and on the attacking prey strategies of the seagulls [22]. To define the location of a new search agent (\vec{F}_s), collision avoidance between search agents in SOA is achieved using the second parameter N .

$$\vec{F}_s = N_x \vec{D}_s(t) \quad (21)$$

In (7), \vec{D}_s , denotes the current seagull location and the existing iteration. The collision avoidance parameter N is modelled as follows:

$$N = E_c - \left(t * \left(\frac{E_c}{Max.Iter} \right) \right) \quad (22)$$

For this, the value of 2 is selected to control the changes in the variable that linearly dropped from E_c to 0. The search agent makes an effort to move close to the position of the ideal individual using (23):

$$\vec{M}_s = A_x (\vec{P}_{bs}(t) - \vec{D}_s(t)) \quad (23)$$

The parameter A is randomized to attain the equilibrium tendency between the exploitation and exploration phases, and is computed by:

$$A = 2 * N^2 * rand() \quad (24)$$

The subsequent changes were made to each location of the search agents:

$$\vec{R}_s = [\vec{F}_s + \vec{M}_s] \quad (25)$$

During their migration, seagulls often change their attacking angle and speed. These behaviors in 3D are defined through the following equations:

$$S' = r * \cos(j) \quad (26)$$

$$T' = r * \sin(j) \quad (27)$$

$$U' = r * j \quad (28)$$

where r refers to the radius of seagulls' spiral movement and the random number selected within $[0, 2]$. The SGOA

technique is applied in initializing the public and secret keys included in the encryption process. The fitness function of SGO for the FOLS method is given by:

$$Fitness\ function = \max \{PSNR\} \quad (29)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This segment inspects the outputs of the SGOA-SCIES approach on 5 test images. Table I portrays a sample visualization of multiple shares generated by the SGOA-SCIES technique on the applied test imaging. The findings suggest that the shares do not convey any significant information pertaining to the original image. The suggested model is simulated by employing Python 3.6.5 tool on PC i5-8600k, 250GB SSD, GeForce 1050Ti 4GB, 16GB RAM, and 1TB HDD. The parameter settings are provided as: learning rate: 0.01, activation: ReLU, epoch count: 50, dropout: 0.5, and batch size: 5. In Figure 2, the outputs indicate that the SGOA-SCIES technique obtains the least MSE values on all images. On IMG-1, the SGOA-SCIES technique obtains decreased MSE of 0.051, while the BDIE-AOFOLS, SSO-HCNN, WOA-HCNN, and GWO-HCNN models obtain improved MSE of 0.0590, 0.0636, 0.1850, and 0.2875, respectively.

TABLE I. VISUALIZATION OF THE MSC SCHEME

Original Image	1 - Share	2 - Share	3 - Share	4 - Share

Fig. 2. MSE outcome of SGOA-SCIES under distinct test images.

Fig. 3. PSNR outcome of SGOA-SCIES under distinct test images.

A detailed comparative analysis of the proposed with recent models [23] model is made. In Figure 3, the outcome exhibits that the SGOA-SCIES method reaches greater PSNR values. On IMG-1 the SGOA-SCIES method attain increased PSNR of 61.055dB while BDIE-AOFOLS, SSO-HCNN, WOA-HCNN, and GWO-HCNN approaches attain lesser PSNR of 60.42dB, 60.10dB, 55.46dB, and 53.54dB, respectively. Similarly, on IMG-5, the SGOA-SCIES approaches attain increased PSNR of 58.002dB while BDIE-AOFOLS, SSO-HCNN, WOA-HCNN, and GWO-HCNN approaches attain reduced PSNR of 57.72dB, 57.65dB, 55.58dB, and 54.48dB, respectively. These outputs ensured the enhanced security accomplishment of the SGOA-SCIES approach over the other techniques.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, a new SGOA-SCIES method is demonstrated for the encryption of the shares in the VANET, aiming to create multiple shares and encrypt them to achieve security. It consists of three operation stages, which are MSC, FOCS-based share encryption, and SGOA-based key generation. In the presented SGOA-SCIES technique, the MSC scheme can be employed to generate multiple sets of shares. For the share encryption process, the SGOA-SCIES algorithm exploits the FOCS method to encrypt the generated shares. The optimal keys of the FOCS technique can be chosen by the use of SGOA which enhances the security level. The performance evaluation of the SGOA-SCIES method is examined on benchmark data. The stimulation outputs depicted the enhanced accomplishment of the SGOA-SCIES approach over other recent methodologies under various measures. The SGOA-SCIES technique may encounter challenges related to scalability and adaptability in dynamic network conditions. Future work for SGOA-SCIES should prioritize improving scalability, tackling dynamic network challenges, and optimizing for broader VANET communication applicability.

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Comparative Study of Radio Resource Distribution Algorithms

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ABSTRACT

The equitable distribution of radio resources among different users in wireless networks is a difficult problem and has attracted the interest of many studies. This study presents the Proportional Fair Q-Learning Algorithm (PFLA) to enable the equitable distribution of radio resources among diverse users through the integration of Q-learning and proportional fairness principles. The PFLA, Round Robin (RR), and Max Throughput (MaxTP) algorithms were compared to evaluate their effectiveness in resource allocation. Performance was measured in terms of sum-rate throughputs and fairness index. The comparison results showed an improvement in the fairness index metrics for PFLA compared to the other algorithms. PFLA showed gains of 11.62 and 43% in the fairness index compared to RR and MaxTP, respectively. These results show that PFLA is more efficient in utilizing available resources, leading to higher overall system throughput and demonstrating its ability to balance performance metrics between users, especially when the number of users increases.

Keywords-radio resource distribution; proportional fair Q-learning algorithm; round robin; max throughput

I. INTRODUCTION

The allocation of radio resources aims to optimize spectrum efficiency while complying with the predefined fairness criteria. Effortless allocation of radio resources is particularly important in wireless communication networks because the available bandwidth is limited and shared between multiple users [1-2]. To make the best use of these resources, it is necessary to use advanced algorithms to allocate them efficiently and fairly among users. Effective resource allocation algorithms can have a significant impact on the performance of wireless networks. By balancing the competing demands of different users, these algorithms can improve network throughput, reduce latency, and enhance overall user experience [3-4]. Moreover, these algorithms can help network operators reduce costs and improve their return on investment by making more efficient use of their available spectrum.

This paper presents the Proportional Fair Q-Learning Algorithm (PFLA) to optimize radio resource allocation in wireless networks by integrating Q-learning and proportional fairness principles. PFLA dynamically adjusts resource allocation based on network feedback using Q-learning, striving for long-term rewards like throughput and fairness. The proposed algorithm fairly balances the overall system throughput among users by considering factors such as channel conditions, queue sizes, and user priorities. This integrated approach enhances system performance while ensuring equitable treatment for all users, surpassing channel-unaware algorithms in wireless communication scenarios. PFLA can have a significant pragmatic impact on daily wireless communications, as it offers a promise of significantly increased network efficiency and can ensure a more equitable allocation of resources between users. Its implementation results in an improved user experience, reduced latency, and smoother connectivity in daily activities, such as faster

downloads and seamless streaming. PFLA was compared to the RR and MaxTP algorithms based on sum-rate throughputs and fairness index. The results showed that RR and MaxTP have limitations with larger user numbers, unlike PFLA, which improves allocation efficiency by considering channel quality and other factors. Incorporating channel conditions and queue sizes, PFLA surpasses RR and MaxTP in wireless network performance and efficiency. This channel- and size-aware strategy is crucial for enhancing wireless data network performance.

II. RELATED WORK

A user pairing technique can be implemented to match users based on their channel conditions and data rate needs and improve fairness among pairs of users by ensuring that those with similar requirements receive equal resource allocation [5-6]. In [7], it was shown that LTE-licensed assisted access achieves proportional fairness with WiFi by adjusting the initial backoff window size or sensing duration and deriving and validating optimal parameter values through simulation experiments. In [8], a deep reinforcement learning-based method was proposed for D2D communication in spectrum sharing, optimizing spectral efficiency and ensuring fairness between network links through resource block scheduling and power control integration. In [9], a decentralized framework was introduced for non-ideal NOMA networks, formulating a clustering algorithm considering cluster sizes and channel gain variations between User Equipment (UE), achieving a balanced α -fair RA framework, and optimizing throughput and fairness through iterative bandwidth and power refinement. In [10], spectrum and power allocation complexities in NOMAs were addressed by formulating principles focusing on Double-Objective Optimization (DOO) to balance the total and minimum rates. Using a power dispersion method, nonconvex DOO problems were converted into Single-Objective Optimization (SOO) ones through global optimal search, prioritizing equal channel gain for Adaptive Proportional Fair (APF) user pairing and optimization restructuring. In [11], a dynamic power allocation scheme was proposed by employing model-free deep reinforcement learning where transmitters adjust transmission power based on collected channel state and quality of service data to maximize a utility function for weighted sum rates, allowing for adaptability for optimal rates or fair scheduling amidst random CSI changes using deep Q-learning. In [12], Federated Learning (FL) was investigated in wireless networks to improve FL model training under limitations such as incomplete CSI and limited local computing resources. This study quantified the training loss gap between the FL client calendar and centralized training, addressing loss reduction through Lyapunov optimization as stochastic optimization. This method integrated a Gauss process regression-based channel prediction method and incorporated client CSI and computing power into planning decisions to mitigate these challenges. In [13], the maximum weight-min fairness was pursued, optimizing LTE-U node retention probability to maximize throughput in both WiFi and LTE-U networks, addressing bandwidth balance with weight factors and solving the optimization challenge through bisection and Laplace transformation inversion methodologies. In [14], non-licensed frequency bands were organized into time slots for

LTE frame transmission, and Small Base Stations (SBSs) reserved these slots at designated Access Points (APs) to prevent overlaps and interference between mobile and WiFi networks, ensuring independent resources via the maintenance cycle method by allocating specific slots for mobile systems and other WiFi operations.

The existing advances in wireless network optimization, while promising, confront challenges in adaptability, scalability, and holistic consideration of dynamic network conditions. These methods, ranging from user pairing techniques to decentralized frameworks and deep reinforcement learning, often face limitations in scaling to larger networks, dynamically adapting to diverse network conditions, and ensuring fairness across varying user requirements. A comprehensive solution that integrates adaptive machine learning techniques with an algorithmic framework can offer a more flexible and adaptive approach to address these shortcomings. Combining reinforcement learning with predictive analytics and considering a broader spectrum of network parameters could dynamically optimize resource allocation, ensuring fairness while adapting to real-time changes and catering to a larger and more diverse user base in wireless networks.

III. CLASSIC SCHEDULERS

A. Round Robin (RR) Scheduling

Fair resource allocation scheduling aims to achieve equitable distribution of resources among multiple users in a wireless communication system. A widely used logical strategy to implement resource fairness involves the recursive application of the RR scheduling scheme. This iterative approach is designed to ensure an equitable distribution of resources to all users, with the overarching objective of maximizing the average resource allocation rate for all users while adhering to specific fairness criteria [15-18]. In this context, the term "fair resources" denotes the principle of equitably distributing available resources, such as time slots or frequency bands, among all active users. This strategy aims to prevent any single user from monopolizing resources and ensures that each user receives an equal share. To implement this approach, the system recursively applies the RR scheduling scheme, which is a well-established method of providing equal access to resources. The primary goal of this strategy is to improve the overall average resource allocation rate for all users. It does so while maintaining fairness, which is often characterized by specific fairness criteria that dictate how resources should be allocated to different users. By striking a balance between resource fairness and maximizing resource allocation rates, this approach contributes to efficient and equitable resource utilization in wireless communication systems.

B. Max Throughput (MaxTP) Scheduling

The MaxTP scheduler aims to maximize the overall throughput of the base station by assigning a user to each channel, allowing the maximum data speed in the current transmission time interval. The Max TP scheduler can operate in both time and frequency fields. In the frequency field, UE is assigned to the highest Channel Quality Indicator (CQI) [19].

In the MaxTP scheduling algorithm, channels are allocated to UEs based on their CQI values. UEs with better channel conditions (higher CQI) are given priority in resource allocation. This prioritization aims to maximize data rates for the UEs, resulting in higher overall throughput for the base station. The MaxTP scheduler can adapt to changing channel conditions and dynamically allocate RBs to UEs, ensuring efficient resource utilization and maximizing throughput. The specific implementation and fine-tuning of the algorithm may vary depending on the network requirements and system parameters.

C. Proportional Fair Scheduling (PFS)

PFS strategies have been developed to achieve a balanced trade-off between various performance metrics, primarily focusing on UE throughput and fairness. These schemes rely on evaluating the indicators of both the current and historical channel quality of the UEs. Specifically, they consider the instantaneous and average data rates experienced by UEs over time to determine a priority function. Within PFS, the scheduler, at each time slot, denoted as t , grants the highest priority to the UE that exhibits the maximum priority function. This priority function, denoted as P_k for the k -th UE, is mathematically expressed as:

$$P_k = \operatorname{argmax} \frac{dr_k(t)}{HR_k(t)} \quad (1)$$

where $dr_k(t)$ represents the instantaneous achievable data rate for the k -th UE when connected to the channel at time slot t . Additionally, $HR_k(t)$ signifies the historical average data rate that has been assigned to the k -th UE up to and including the time slot t . In the PFS scheduling scheme, the system executes a two-step process using feedback from channel quality indicators. First, it calculates the priority functions for all UEs and sorts them in descending order. Subsequently, channels are assigned to the UE with the highest priority function. This process ensures a fair distribution of resources among UEs while considering their channel qualities, which in turn aids in optimizing overall network performance. In PFS scheduling algorithm, the priority function P_k is calculated based on the ratio of the current achievable data rate to the past average data rate for each UE. This prioritization ensures that UEs with varying channel conditions and data rate histories are allocated RBs fairly, balancing throughput and fairness.

IV. THE PROPOSED MODEL

A. Definitions and Terminologies

This study considers WiFi networks, where different algorithms can be employed in managing access and resource allocation among devices to ensure fair transmission opportunities. This study considered a wireless network configuration consisting of two primary sets: $N = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, representing a group of agents, and $K = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$, representing a collection of available channels. Agents use a random access protocol to send their data over these shared channels. At each discrete time slot, each agent could choose one channel for transmission with an associated transmission probability such as an Aloha-type narrowband transmission scheme. It is assumed that all agents always have pending packets for transmission. After each time slot t , when an agent i

attempts to send a packet, it receives binary feedback in the form of an ACK signal denoted as $o_i(t)$. This signal indicates whether their transmission was successful or not. If $o_i(t) = 1$, it means that transmission was successful. On the other hand, $o_i(t) = 0$ signifies a failed transmission or collision.

Let $a_i(t) \in \{0, 1, \dots, K\}$ denote the action taken by agent i at the time slot t . Here, $a_i(t) = 0$ corresponds to the scenarios where agent i chooses not to transmit a packet during the time slot t , potentially to mitigate network congestion. On the contrary, $a_i(t) = k$, where $1 \leq k \leq K$, denotes the i -th agent's decision to transmit a packet on channel k in time slot t . During real-time operation, each agent, denoted as i , makes autonomous decisions independently and in a distributed manner. These decisions aim to acquire efficient spectrum access policies exclusively through ACK signals. Traditional methods for solving this problem become intractable from a mathematical point of view as the network size grows, given its combinatorial nature and the challenge of dealing with partial-state observations. The Q-learning approach was embraced due to its ability to provide satisfactory approximate solutions, even when confronted with large state and action spaces.

B. Q-Learning Approach

The action taken by an agent i at time step t is represented by $a_i(t)$, where $a_i(t) \in \{\text{Transmit}, \text{Wait}\}$. The *Transmit* action indicates that the agent i initiates transmission, while the *Wait* action indicates that the agent refrains from transmitting. The observation of the channel state at time step t is described as $O_i(t)$ and can have one of the three possible values: $O_i(t) = \{\text{Success}, \text{Collision}, \text{Idleness}\}$. The *Success* observation indicates that a single station has successfully transmitted on the channel, *Collision* indicates that multiple stations have transmitted simultaneously resulting in a collision, and *Idleness* indicates that no station is currently transmitting. The agent analyzes the acknowledgment received from the Access Point (AP) when it transmits and monitors the channel while waiting to determine the value of $O_i(t)$. The channel state at time step t is defined as an action-observation pair called $c_t = (a_i(t), O_i(t))$. The channel state c_t can have five possible combinations: $\{\text{Transmit}, \text{Success}\}$, $\{\text{Transmit}, \text{Collision}\}$, $\{\text{Wait}, \text{Success}\}$, $\{\text{Wait}, \text{Collision}\}$, and $\{\text{Wait}, \text{Idleness}\}$. The environmental state s_t contains the history of the action-observation pairs for a specified length of M , which determines the scope of historical data considered by the agent. When the action $a_i(t)$ is executed, the transition from state s_t to state s_{t+1} generates the reward r_{t+1} , where:

$$r_{t+1} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } z_t = \text{Success} \\ 0, & \text{if } z_t = \text{Collision or Idleness} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Let $r_i(t)$ denote the reward received by agent i at the beginning of the time slot t . This reward depends on the actions of agent i at the previous time slot, $a_i(t-1)$, and the actions of other agents at the previous time slot, $a_{-i}(t-1)$, which collectively form the elusive network state that agent i is trying to identify. The cumulative discounted reward, denoted by R_i , is calculated as follows:

$$R_i = \sum_{t=1}^T \gamma^{t-1} r_i(t) \quad (3)$$

where $0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$ serves as a discounting factor, and T represents the time horizon. Typically, γ is set to 1, but it may assume a value less than 1 when T is bounded or unbounded. Following an occurrence of a state-action pair (s_t, a_t) and the subsequent reward r_{t+1} , Q-learning updates the Q-function, represented as (s_t, a_t) , through the application of the following update rule:

$$q(s_t, a_t) \leftarrow q(s_t, a_t) + \alpha * (r_{t+1} + \gamma * \max_{a'} q(s_{t+1}, a') - q(s_t, a_t)) \quad (4)$$

where r_{t+1} is the immediate reward obtained after taking action a_t in state s_t , $\max_{a'} q(s_{t+1}, a')$ is the maximum Q value over all possible actions in the next state s_{t+1} and represents the estimated future cumulative reward, $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ signifies the learning rate that governs the magnitude of the update, and γ is a constant between 0 and 1 called the discount factor that determines the importance of future awards. The Q-function is updated iteratively to reflect the acquired reward and the expected future rewards based on the highest Q-value associated with potential future actions. During the period when the Q-function (s, a) is being updated, the decision-making process operates based on this evolving Q-function. A common policy strategy in this context is the ϵ -greedy policy. Under the ϵ -greedy policy, the agent selects the action that maximizes the Q-value, denoted as:

$$a_t = \operatorname{argmax}_a (s_t, a') \quad (5)$$

In contrast, with a probability of ζ , the agent selects a random action. The rationale behind incorporating randomness through ζ is to strike a balance between exploration and exploitation, enabling the agent to explore new actions while also favoring actions with known high Q-values.

C. Proportional Fair Q-Learning for Dynamic Resource Allocation

Combining Q-learning with the proportional fair algorithm for dynamic resource allocation between users and channels in wireless communication systems can enhance system performance and fairness. The following assumptions were made:

- Multiple users (indexed by i) and multiple channels (indexed by k).
- Each user has a Q-table to learn the Q-values for each state-action pair (state: user's buffer size and channel conditions, action: channel allocation).

Initialize Q-tables for each user, with dimensions (s, a) , where s represents the state and a represents the action. Initialize all Q-values to zero. The algorithm shown in Figure 1 uses Q-learning to learn the optimal channel allocation strategy based on observed states and rewards. The fairness factor λ is introduced to ensure proportional fairness in the allocation of resources. Users strike a balance between exploration and exploitation through the ϵ -greedy policy.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Numerical experiments were carried out in Matlab to determine the performance attributes of PFLA. The simulated wireless network was designed to encompass a variable number

of users, denoted as N , ranging between 5 and 50, and K channels, varying between 2 and 23. A consistent channel bandwidth, denoted as $B = 25\text{MHz}$, was maintained to calculate data rates.

```

Input:  $\alpha, \gamma, \epsilon, \lambda, M$  (Maximum number of iterations).
Output: Learning values,  $Q_{m \times n}$ 

Begin
Initialize  $Q_{m \times n}(s_t, a_t)$  to 0 for all state-action pairs  $(s_t, a_t)$ .
Generate a random number  $\xi$  in  $[0, 1]$ 
Set  $s_t$  to a random state from the state set:
 $S = \{\text{Success}, \text{Collision}, \text{Idleness}\}$ .
Set  $act_t$  to a random action from the action set:
 $S = \{\text{Transmit}, \text{Wait}\}$ .
Generate a random number  $x$  in  $[0, 1]$ .
for iteration  $m = 1, \dots, M$  do
  for time-slot  $t = 1, \dots, T$  do
    for agent  $i = 1, \dots, N$  do
      if agent  $i$  has still data to send do
        Determine the state of the robot  $s_i(t)$ .
        If  $x < \xi$  then
          Choose  $a_i(t)$  based on (4)
        else
          Choose the best  $a_i(t) \in \{0, \dots, K\}$  using  $Q_{m \times n}$ .
        End if
        Perform action  $a_i(t)$  and receive reward  $r_i(t)$ .
        Update Q-values using Q-learning:
        Calculate the TD error:
 $\delta = r + \gamma * \max(s', a') - \max(s, a)$ 
        Update Q-value:  $(s, a) \leftarrow (s, a) + \alpha * \delta$ 
 $s_i(t) \leftarrow s_i(t+1)$ 
      End if
    End for
  End for
End for
Return  $Q_{m \times n}$ 
End

```

Fig. 1. PFL algorithm for dynamic resource allocation.

A. Sum-Rate Throughput

The average rate of each UE in the T schedule interval is defined by:

$$AR_i = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T dr_i(t) \quad (6)$$

The sum rate is established as a specific metric to measure the optimization. It quantifies the average cumulative throughput of the entire network during the period of the schedule interval T :

$$R_{sum} = \sum_{i=1}^N AR_i \quad (7)$$

Based on Figure 1, the results show the sum rate throughput achieved by different scheduling methods for different users. In PFLA, with increasing user numbers, total sum rates tend to increase, demonstrating effective resource allocation based on the Q-learning approach. RR scheduling shows a less consistent trend and does not match PFLA performance for more users. The MaxTP scheduler starts with a competitive sum rate throughput, but as the number of users increases, the performance plateaus. MaxTP does not adapt well to the growing number of users, indicating limitations in resource

allocation efficiency. In general, PFLA is more effective in resource allocation in this scenario, with a higher number of users resulting in better average throughput than other methods. RR and MaxTP schedulers have limitations in handling large user numbers, which leads to less efficient resource utilization.

Fig. 2. Sum-rate throughputs for PFLA, RR, and MaxTP.

B. Fairness Index

Fairness can be evaluated using Jain's fairness index. In the following equation, n represents the total number of users and x_i is the total amount of throughput obtained by each user:

$$J(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \frac{(\sum_{k=1}^n T_k)^2}{N(\sum_{k=1}^n T_k^2)} \quad (8)$$

Figure 3 shows the fairness index achieved by different scheduling methods for different numbers of users.

Fig. 3. Comparative analysis of fairness metrics.

Fairness is often measured by a fairness index, and in this case, higher values indicate better fairness. PFLA consistently shows a high level of fairness for all users. With the increase in the number of users, the fairness index is still relatively stable, showing that PFLA maintains equality between users while efficiently allocating resources. The RR scheduler shows relatively low fairness indexes, which decrease as the number of users increases. MaxTP scheduling starts with moderately competitive fairness indexes, but as user numbers increase, fairness decreases. Like RR scheduling, it is difficult to maintain fairness when more users are needed to serve. In summary, PFLA consistently achieved the highest fairness index, demonstrating its ability to balance performance metrics between users, especially if the system has more users. The RR

and MaxTP schedulers provide a certain degree of fairness, but their flexibility decreases as users increase.

The following formulas were used to determine the relative advantages of PFLA over RR and MaxTP:

$$Gain_{PFLA-RR} = \frac{PFLA \text{ average fairness index} - RR \text{ average fairness index}}{PFLA \text{ average fairness index}} \times 100$$

$$Gain_{PFLA-RR} = \frac{0.86 - 0.76}{0.86} \times 100 \approx 11.62\%$$

$$Gain_{PFLA-MaxTP} = \frac{PFLA \text{ average fairness index} - MaxTP \text{ average fairness index}}{PFLA \text{ average fairness index}} \times 100$$

$$Gain_{PFLA-MaxTP} = \frac{(0.86 - 0.49)}{0.86} \times 100 \approx 43\%$$

VI. CONCLUSION

The choice of an algorithm for radio resource allocation depends on the specific requirements and constraints of the wireless communication network. PFLA aims to maximize system throughput by considering both channel conditions and queue sizes. By incorporating channel conditions and queue sizes into the resource allocation decision-making process, PFLA outperforms the RR and MaxTP algorithms in terms of performance and efficiency in wireless networks. The empirical findings showed an improvement in the fairness index metrics when comparing PFLA with the RR and MaxTP algorithms. The percentage gain between PFLA and RR was determined to be 11.62%, which represents a notable improvement in the fairness index achieved by PFLA over RR. Similarly, when PFLA was compared to MaxTP, a substantial gain of 43% was achieved in the fairness index, indicating the superior fairness achieved by the proposed algorithm in all the experimental scenarios considered. By extending PFLA to support the unique requirements of next-generation wireless technologies, the proposed allocation algorithm can remain relevant and effective in the ever-evolving landscape of wireless communication. Future work involves further development and adaptation of PFLA to align with the specific demands of emerging wireless technologies, such as 6G and IoT networks, ensuring its applicability and optimization for evolving communication paradigms.

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Efficiency and Durability Assessment of Soil Stabilization using Waste Tire Shreds

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ABSTRACT

Tire waste constitutes an undesirable surplus within urban industrial contexts, presenting a persistent annual increase on a global scale. Consequently, the reduction of tire waste through alternative approaches has attracted the interest of researchers around the world. This study evaluated the efficacy of using tire shreds as soil stabilizers to enhance the strength properties of the mixture in three proportions. Tire shred content of 10, 20, and 30% resulted in reduced CBR values of 3.3, 2.98, and 2.3%, respectively, compared to 4.4% without tire shred content. In addition, the direct shear test revealed that the increase in tire shred content significantly increased shear stress, as 10, 20, and 30% tire shred content resulted in 82.25, 84.14, and 85.87 kPa, respectively. Consequently, tire pieces can be used along with soil as an alternative mixture material in retaining structures.

Keywords-soil stabilization; tire shreds; CBR; shear stress

I. INTRODUCTION

Clay and silt are relatively common forms of soil found throughout the world and are often used to build soil structures such as slopes and highway embankments [1-2]. Building on a weak natural fine-grained subgrade soil could result in major damage and reduced service life of the earthen structure [3]. It is well-recognized that soil stabilization can improve the engineering qualities of soil. One of the most prevalent ways of soil remediation is the practice of mixing tire shreds with the soil [4-9]. Approximately millions of tires are discarded annually from the utilization cycle and deposited in natural environments. The disposal of waste tires poses substantial environmental, health, and safety risks to densely populated contemporary societies [10-11]. Various methods have been employed for the management of waste tires, including, but not limited to, recycling, incineration, and landfilling, and some of them can harm the environment [12-18].

In this context, the industrial reuse of waste tires is important and has attracted considerable attention from many researchers [19-20]. Tire chips, tire powder, shredded tire, tire crumb, tire polishing, and more advanced procedures are used to transform scrap tires into fragments of various shapes and sizes. These materials offer unique properties that improve the quality of geotechnical works, such as durability, strength, lightness, compaction, drainage, and high frictional resistance [21-22]. As a result, mixing these materials with low-shear soil can address geotechnical issues faced by civil engineers, in addition to providing an economical solution to environmental problems [8, 23]. Many studies have investigated the shear strength characteristics of sand and rubber mixtures, underlining the importance of adding some rubber to the sand to increase its shear strength affected by various criteria such as normal stress, tire content, tire aspect ratio, tire length, sand matrix unit weight, and compaction [24-26].

Tire shreds are used tires that have been shredded by a shredder cutter. Several different types of machinery are available for this activity. The size of the tire chips is determined mainly by the equipment. The resulting chopped pieces are generally uneven in shape, with larger dimensions being 2-4 times larger than smaller dimensions, ranging from 1 to 2.38 mm [13, 27]. Large earthwork projects that use recycled tires, such as highway construction, are an ideal application for shredded tires because there is the potential to use large quantities while improving or maintaining the performance of the earthen structure [28-31]. Determining the dry density and optimum moisture content of the materials is one of the fundamental preliminary steps required to enable proper compaction of the various layers of the road. The use of clay soil and tire scrap mix for road construction depends on supplying the highest dry density and optimal moisture content in various tire shred content ratios [20, 31]. The waste tire is available in powder and granule forms, both of which are plentiful and allow for a uniform soil mix [32, 33]. This study investigated the optimal content of Duhok clay granule mix and tire waste shred, using an experimental plan, soil and tire waste characterization and classification tests, and presenting relations for use in engineering applications. This study aimed to evaluate the practicality of tire waste in improving soil quality, promoting sustainable development, and its influence on shear strength, compaction, and CBR when combined with clay soils.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

The clay soil used in this study was collected in Duhok governorate (36° 59' 24.5"N, 42° 39' 20.7"E) in Northern Iraq. The properties of clay soil are shown in Table I according to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS) [34].

TABLE I. CHARACTERIZATION TEST RESULTS OF CLAY

Properties	Value
Optimum moisture content (%)	17.7
Plastic limit (%)	26
Maximum dry density (g.cm ³)	1.778
CBR (%)	4.4
Classification	Well graded

Fig. 1. The tire shreds used in this study.

Tire shreds crafted from discarded tires were used in this study according to [35]. These tires were shredded in a specialized facility that handles old and spare tires obtained from the Zakho Ibrahim Khalil plant. The tire grinding and screening process yielded fiber-like pellets with various shapes, called "shreds", each measuring approximately 1/3 inch in size, as shown in Figure 1. The samples used in the experiments had varied amounts of tire shreds: 10%, 20%, and 30%.

B. Methods

Experimental tests were carried out to examine how tire buffing and tire powder impact the strength parameters of sand. This study focused on specimens with 5% water content, varying the percentages of tire buffing and powder at 10, 20, and 30%. The addition of rubber grains to the sand results in a decrease in the unit weight of the mixture. The grain size analysis test (sieve and hydrometer) evaluates soil grain size percentages and the distribution of larger particles, following ASTM procedure D422-63 [36]. Figure 2 shows the grain-size distribution curve. Atterberg limit tests were performed on untreated soils using ASTM procedures D423-66 and D424-59 for liquid and plastic limits, respectively. The liquid limit defines the moisture content at which the soil changes from liquid to plastic [37]. Based on the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and Maximum Dry Density (MDD) of each mixture, determined by the Proctor compaction test, the required amounts of dry soil and tire shreds were produced according to the ASTM D1157 procedure [38].

Fig. 2. Grain size distribution curve of the soil.

To find the ideal tire shred content range for improved California Bearing Ratio (CBR) values, CBR tests were carried out using cylindrical samples according to ASTM D1883-16 [39]. CBR values were calculated by exerting pressure on the soil with a cylindrical piston. The piston was inserted into the soil at a constant speed. The CBR values for each soil sample were determined by dividing the measured load by the standard stress for penetrations of 2.5 and 5 mm. Each experiment was repeated twice to verify consistency and the CBR was determined by:

$$CBR = (P_t/P_s) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where P_t is the corrected test load corresponding to the chosen penetration from the load penetration curve, and P_s is the

standard load for the same depth of penetration. A series of direct shear tests were performed to determine the drained shear strength parameters of sand. This study used rectangular samples as shown in Figure 3. Within the testing apparatus, a vertical normal force, denoted as N , was applied to the top of the box, while a horizontal force, denoted as T , exerted shear action on the specimen along a thin plane between the two halves of the box, acting on the upper part of the box. Following [40], each sample with dimensions of $4 \times 4 \times 2.2$ cm was subjected to shear strength testing under three different normal stresses of 1, 2, and 4 kN/m² to determine shear strength parameters. To establish a drained condition, the rate of shear deformation was set to 1.5 mm/min. The determination of the direct shear test proceeded as follows:

$$\text{Corrected Area} = A = A_o \times (1 - \delta/3) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Shear load} = P =$$

$$\text{Proving ring reading} \times \text{Proving ring constant} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Shear stress } \tau = P/A \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3. The specimen of direct shear stress test.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The compaction test revealed a distinct inverse relationship between the tire shred content and the modified compaction results. Without tire shred content (0%), the dry unit weight was 1.778 g/cm³, with a 17.7% OMC. When tire shreds were added to the mixture in proportions of 10, 20, and 30%, the dry unit weight and optimal moisture content decreased to 1.657 g/cm³ and 15.6%, 1.571 g/cm³ and 12.7%, and 1.504 g/cm³ and 11.8%, respectively. This means that as the percentage of tire shred increases, there is a consistent reduction in dry unit weight and a decrease in the optimal moisture content during the modified compaction test. The significance of the CBR test lies in evaluating tire shreds' impact on the soil. CBR was 4.4% without tire shred content. As tire shreds were incorporated into the mixture at 10, 20, and 30%, the CBR values exhibited a decrease reaching 3.3, 2.98, and 2.3%, respectively, as shown in Figure 4. This assessment extends to the Modified Compaction Test and MDD, illustrating how tire shreds increase air space, hinder water absorption, reduce soil stiffness, and weaken the bond between tire shreds and soil particles.

The swell test was used after the CBR test to ensure its result. The initial swell measurement, without tire shred content, was 1.97%. Adding tire shred at 10, 20, and 30% proportions, the swell increased to 2.68, 3.06, and 3.65%, respectively. Tire shred increases the air void in the soil, which causes the swell to expand, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 4. CBR values of soil with tire shreds.

Fig. 5. Swell values of soil with tire shreds.

The results of the direct shear test illustrate a clear trend. With no tire shred content, the recorded shear stress value was 75 kPa. Adding tire shreds to the mixture in proportions of 10, 20, and 30% increased shear stress to 82.25, 84.14, and 85.87 kPa, respectively. Figure 6 shows the relation between normal and shear stress. These findings underscore the direct relationship between increasing tire shred content and increased shear stress. This can be attributed to the contrasting material properties, with the soil being brittle and the tire shreds being ductile. Consequently, the mixture becomes more ductile, resulting in increased shear stress, as the direct shear test is more sensitive to ductile materials compared to brittle ones. Furthermore, the inverse relationship between CBR and the direct shear test results signifies the interplay between the two test methods in assessing material behavior. The cohesiveness test showed that cohesiveness started at 8.71 kPa with zero tire shred content, reduced to 5.79 kPa with 10% tire shred, increased to 7.08 kPa with 20% tire shred, and reached 11.02 kPa with 30% tire shred content. Comparatively, in the triaxial compression test, the angle of the internal friction of sand, as determined by direct shear and strain tests, showed an increase of 2-8°. In the direct shear test shown in Figure 7, the angle of friction was 33.4° without tire shred, 37.2° with 10% tire shred, 37.2° with 20% tire shred, and 34.5° with 30% tire shred. These data illustrate the proportional increase in the angle of friction with increasing tire shred content.

Fig. 6. Relationship between normal and shear stress.

Fig. 7. Relationship between tire shreds (%) and angle of internal friction.

Therefore, as the percentage of tire shred content increased, there was a consistent decrease in dry unit weight and optimal moisture content during the modified compaction test. As the tire shred content increased in the mixture in proportions of 10, 20, and 30%, the CBR values exhibited a decrease, reaching 3.3, 2.98, and 2.3%, respectively, as shown in Figure 4. This evaluation extends to the modified compaction test and MDD, illustrating how tire shreds increase air space, hinder water absorption, reduce soil stiffness, and weaken the bond between tire shreds and soil particles. The swell test after the CBR test validated the CBR result. The initial swell measurement was 1.97% without tire shreds, and by adding tire shreds in proportions of 10, 20, and 30%, the swell increased by 2.68, 3.06, and 3.65%, respectively. Tire shreds increase the air void in the soil, which causes the swell to expand, as shown in Figure 5.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the impact of strengthening stabilized soil using tire shreds in various proportions, reaching the following conclusions:

- The study used experimental and analytical methods to investigate the use of a higher tire shred percentage, ranging from 10% to 30%. This contrasts with a prior study that examined a lower tire percentage, ranging from 2% to 15%.
- The importance of the CBR test is to determine how tire shreds affect the soil when their proportion is zero (4.4%). The CBR decreased to 3.3, 2.98, and 2.3% when adding 10, 20, and 30% tire shred content, respectively.

- The decrease in test results can be attributed to soil particles having a higher density than tire particles, which subsequently reduces the OMC. Additionally, the presence of tires increases the void ratio within the soil, resulting in a decrease in the CBR rate.
- The results of the direct shear test when using 10, 20, and 30% tire shred were 82.25, 84.14, and 85.87 kPa. These results highlight a distinct relationship between increased shear stress and tire shred content.
- The incorporation of a higher proportion of tire shreds as soil reinforcement resulted in a reduction in brittleness due to their increased ductility. Additionally, the inclusion of tire shreds mitigated the loss of stiffness caused by alternating wetting and drying cycles, in contrast to the low percentage of tire shreds, leading to an improvement in soil hardness and strength.
- Tire shreds are lightweight materials, and as their proportion in the soil mixture increases, the soil properties are diminished. Consequently, tire shred pieces can be used alongside soil as an alternative material in retaining structures.

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An Improved Machine Learning Method by applying Cloud Forensic Meta-Model to Enhance the Data Collection Process in Cloud Environments

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing has revolutionized the way businesses operate by offering accuracy in Normalized Mutual Information (NMI). However, with the growing adoption of cloud services, ensuring the accuracy and validation of common processes through machine learning and clustering of these common concepts as well as of the processes generated by cloud forensics experts' data in cloud environments has become a paramount concern. The current paper proposes an innovative approach to enhance the data collection procedure in cloud environments by applying a Cloud Forensic Meta-Model (CFMM) and integrating it with machine learning techniques to improve the cloud forensic data. Through this approach, consistency and compatibility across different cloud environments in terms of accuracy are ensured. This research contributes to the ongoing efforts to validate the clustering process for data collection in cloud computing environments and advance the field of cloud forensics for standardizing the representation of cloud forensic data, certifying NMI and accuracy across different cloud environments.

Keywords-cloud forensics; data collection; cloud environment; cloud computing; data integrity

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing has transformed the landscape of IT infrastructure, enabling businesses to harness the benefits of scalable, efficient, accurate, and flexible resources [1]. However, as organizations increasingly migrate their critical data and applications to cloud environments, concerns about data security, integrity, and the ability to effectively investigate and respond to accurate data collection incidents have grown due to redundancy during the interoperability process regarding NMI [2, 3]. Establishing the trustworthiness of accurate data collection in cloud environments is essential and it necessitates the development of innovative approaches that not only enhance data collection, but also enable intelligent analysis and proactive validation process [4]. Numerous studies introduced an improved Machine Learning (ML) method that leverages

the Cloud Forensic Meta-Model (CFMM) to significantly ameliorate the data collection process in cloud environments but accuracy issues, such as classifications and NMI emerge [5, 6]. Traditional data collection practices in the cloud often lack the structured and standardized approach needed to address data collection, validation, and accuracy concerns comprehensively [7]. The integration of CFMM with ML for data collection offers a promising solution to these setbacks. The adoption of cloud computing has introduced unique challenges to data collection and validation [8, 9]. Traditional methods and tools designed for on-premises environments are often ill-suited for cloud-based systems. Cloud environments are dynamic, distributed, and virtualized, making data collection and analysis a complex and costly endeavor [10]. Additionally, the dynamic nature of accurate data collection in

cloud systems makes tracking data provenance and maintaining the integrity of critical information rigorous.

Fig. 1. Cloud forensic process.

Furthermore, Figure 1 explains the Cloud Forensic (CF) process divided into the ML techniques that are integrated into several procedures to enable intelligent data analysis, anomaly detection, and predictive analytics. ML meta-models can automatically identify patterns, anomalies, and potential validation extortions in real-time interoperability process by enhancing the proactive accuracy posture of cloud environments [11, 12]. Not only does this integration strengthen the ability to detect and manage to validate data collection promptly, but also provides valuable insights for forensic investigations [13].

In this study, we present the development of a prototype system that implements CFMM and integrates ML algorithms for data analysis to improve accuracy in terms of NMI. The system is rigorously evaluated in a simulated cloud environment employing various use cases and scenarios applied for classification. The results of this research indicate substantial improvements in data collection, accuracy, and the ability to detect and respond to NMI [14] incidents proactively. Problems related to the classification performed during the digital investigation process in cloud environments lead to a discussion of incident response strategies [15, 16]. Some of them propose new tools, procedures, and meta-models to accomplish accurate data collection investigation in the cloud [17, 18]. In summary, by introducing an improved ML method and by applying a CF meta-model, this article contributes to an enhanced data collection process in cloud environments. The critical need for upgraded data collection procedures in cloud environments is tackled by proposing an innovative method that combines the CFMM and ML techniques to ensure NMI. The main target of this paper is to propose a forensic model to organize and structure a CF field among forensic domains. The proposed abstract model combines and unifies redundant and different common CF processes and terminologies from different CF models.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Cloud Forensics and Investigations

Previous research has extensively explored challenges such as classification regarding NMI [19, 20]. Authors in [21] provided an overview of various forensic techniques and

approaches in cloud environments, offering valuable insights into the field of establishing NMI. Digital forensics in cloud computing environments face unique difficulties related to data collection, preservation, and analysis, laying the foundation for the need to develop structured models [22-24].

Data provenance in cloud meta-model environment plays a crucial role in forensic investigations [25]. Research on data provenance in cloud environments explores methods for tracking data lineage and warranting its integrity, which aligns with the goals of the proposed CFMM approach. ML for anomaly detection in cloud data collection has been widely applied in cloud data classifications [26, 27]. Studies on anomaly classification and data collection using ML techniques [28-30] can inform the integration of such methods with CFMM to enhance data collection process and accuracy. Standardization efforts in cloud data classification bodies and organizations [31, 32] have proposed guidelines and standards for cloud classification and forensics. These standards can inform the development of CFMM and its compatibility with existing best practices on a medium and large scale.

B. Cloud NMI and Compliance Frameworks

Various frameworks and models, like the Cloud NMI Matrix [33], provide guidelines for the classification of cloud environments [34]. Understanding these frameworks can help in designing CFMM to align with industry best practices. Research on cloud metadata management and studies in cloud environments can provide insights into the types of metadata that are crucial for forensic investigations [35]. The proposed CFMM's reliance on forensic metadata makes these studies relevant. Cloud incident response framework research can elucidate the data collection, analysis, and response phases, which are integral to CFMM's objectives. Forensic tools and platforms have also emerged to address the unique challenges of cloud environments. Research on these methods can identify gaps that CFMM aims to fill. Although much research has been conducted on CF, a large scale systematic review on the challenges, solutions, and methodologies does not exist [36]. On the other hand, as far as cloud services are concerned, they have not been given the proper attention even though they are the most important aspects in the field, since cloud computing is based on the services offered [37]. Software designers and engineers, in many cases do not design and implement cloud services to be cloud forensic and enabled for accurate data collection. This is a major issue in CF investigation since the former cannot be conducted in a forensically data collection accurate manner [38, 39].

Authors in [40, 41] proposed various investigation models for the CF domain. However, the models suggested are limited in scope and do not encompass the entire CF field. Therefore, other researchers [42, 43] point out the need for a unified model to include all CF terms with an organized data collection process [44]. These works collectively offer a foundation for the CFMM development and integration. They underscore the significance of structured data collection, data provenance, and the application of ML in addressing the challenges posed by cloud environments, contributing to the growing body of knowledge regarding the accuracy in CF.

III. METHODOLOGY

Data collection and processing in CFMM often involves working with datasets to analyze and investigate data collection incidents or forensic cases in cloud computing environments. A step-by-step overview of how data collection and processing can be conducted using datasets within the CFMM follows.

A. Clustering Process using Datasets and Concept Datasets

To reduce the redundant complexity of the existing evidential clustering data and so improve the accuracy in terms of data collection, a new alternative version, named CFMM is proposed in this paper. CFMM is based on the following two expectations:

- For the same data set, the centers obtained in the partition and those of singleton clusters are very similar. This means that the meta-clusters can be ignored in the initial iterations because the centers of meta-clusters are defined based on the instant information of the related redundant clusters.
- Some of the objects in the dataset are difficult to be accurately assigned to specific clusters. They are then assigned to the related meta-clusters composed of only several close specific clusters. Thus, it is not necessary to expose all the objects under the power-dataset.

By the above assumptions, the CFMM method can be summarized as: (1) preliminary sorting partition, (2) partial organization data rearrangement.

B. Data sorting and Organization

The purposes of this subsection are to preliminary sort and assign each object in the dataset as the outlier, precise or imprecise, adaptively. To derive such a proposal, let us consider a query set X including n objects in p dimensions with $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_c\}$. The support degrees of each object belonging to different singleton (specific) cluster and the noise cluster, called the mass of beliefs in specific partition, can be minimized by an FCM-like objective function at first. There are many methods to obtain the mass of beliefs. For example, the noise clustering method can be applied for the dataset, and we have modified it as the version of the specific partial organization data arrangement to facilitate the presentation. The objective function can be expressed as:

$$JDEC - NC(M1, V1) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^c \beta_{ij} \cdot d_{ij}^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i \cdot m_i \phi \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^c \beta_{ij} + m_i \phi = 1, \forall i = 1, n \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^c \beta_{ij} + m_i \phi = 1, \forall i = 1, n \quad (3)$$

where $M1 = (m_1, \dots, m_n) \in R^{n \times (|\Omega|+1)}$ is the mass of the belief matrix for n objects in X , and $V1 \in R^{c \times p}$ is the matrix of the centers of single clusters. d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance between the object x_i and the center of singleton cluster ω_j . Parameters β, δ are adjustable.

This research utilized four distinct datasets, each sourced from separate investigations by the Brazilian Federal Police Department. These datasets, originally in varied formats, were converted to a consistent plain text format and underwent extensive preprocessing in order to be prepared for analysis. To assess the quality of the data partitions, each dataset was

compared against a "ground truth" reference partition, established by an expert in the field. This comparison was crucial in evaluating the data's organizational structure and its relevance to the study's objectives. The datasets were quantitatively characterized using several metrics, as detailed in Table I, namely the number of documents (N), groups (G), attributes (A), singletons (S), and the distribution of documents across groups. For instance, Dataset A included 37 documents across 23 groups, with an attribute count of 1744 and 12 singletons, the largest group comprising 3 documents. Dataset B, contained 111 documents in 49 groups, with a significantly higher attribute count of 7894 and 28 singletons. This analytical approach provided in-depth insight into the structural and thematic elements of the documents, offering a comprehensive understanding of the data.

TABLE I. DATASET CHARACTERISTICS

Dataset	N	G	A	S	Largest cluster
A	37	23	1744	12	3
B	111	49	7894	28	12
C	68	40	2699	24	8
D	74	38	5095	26	17

Utilizing several meta-modeling methodologies, we were able to validate the generated datasets consistency as well as their applicability (comparison against other models, frequency-based selection). Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the built FCMM is consistent and coherent. This allows domain forensic practitioners to simply instantiate new solution models by picking and combining concept elements (attributes and operations) based on the requirements of their models. From a scientific perspective, the use of reference partitions for evaluating data clustering algorithms is considered a principled approach. In controlled experimental settings, reference partitions are usually obtained from data generated synthetically according to some probability distributions. From a practical standpoint, reference partitions are usually acquired in a different way, but they are still employed to choose a particular clustering algorithm that is more appropriate for a given application, or to calibrate its parameters. In our case, parameter partitions were constructed by a domain expert and reflect the expectations that (S) has about the clusters that should be found in the datasets. In this sense, the evaluation method that we used to assess the obtained data partitions is based on the Adjusted Rand Index, which measures the agreement between a partition P, attained from running a clustering algorithm, and the reference partition given by the expert examiner. More specifically, the greater its value, the better the agreement between P and R is.

Table II elucidates the stratification of processes into five discrete clusters using the CFMM methodology, further delineating into 30 principal categories. The dataset systematically organizes the sequences of actions within a protocol tailored for incident response and data governance. The inaugural cluster delineates the preliminary arrangements and the pinpointing of evidence. The subsequent cluster, Cluster 2, is dedicated to data verification and authentication, with a pronounced consideration for privacy. The third cluster is centered around data analysis and structuring, incorporating procedural steps for system deployment. Cluster 4 is exhaustive

in its detail on the collection phase, encapsulating data acquisition and the safeguarding of digital evidence. Culminating the clusters, Cluster 5 is comprehensive of documentation and reporting mechanisms, safeguarding of records, and the presentation of findings, signifying a meticulous blueprint for incident management and regulatory compliance.

TABLE II. CLUSTERING CHARACTERISTICS

Sequence No	Processes	Cluster Number
1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-preparation Pre-incident data collection Incident detection Initial response Identification Evidence source identification Log collection 	1
2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Verifications Authenticating Confirmation Data validation Incident confirmation Concurrent activities Privacy 	2
3	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Data analyzing Analysis Implementation on open stack Organization Matching Examination 	3
4	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Collection Data acquisition Data extraction Collect digital evidence Gathering data Storage 	4
5	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Documentation Reporting Preservation Presentation 	5

Fig. 2. CFMM partition results.

In Figure 3, the flowchart of the adaptive CFMM partitioning can be seen. By doing this, one can easily find that only a few objects need to be further reassigned. It can greatly reduce the computational complexity, with each imprecise object having a specific dynamic edited forensic meta-model.

The diagram outlines a structured framework for data classification within a CFMM designed to optimize the sorting of data elements. The process commences with the introduction of the data set into the system, which then undergoes evaluation using a clustering function. The mass of belief (*Bel*) for the object *i* is assigned to the cluster \emptyset or ω . This function determines a *Bel* for each data element, reflecting its affinity to a particular cluster. Data elements whose *Bel* strongly surpasses the threshold are confidently allocated to a cluster, while those with less definitive scores are marked as imprecise and set aside for further analysis.

Fig. 3. CFMM partitioning process.

This initial sorting results in a preliminary categorization, separating data elements into precise and imprecise groups. Precise elements are those with clear cluster alignment, whereas imprecise elements undergo a more detailed review. A specialized dynamic edited forensic meta-model is then employed to reassess the imprecise elements, considering their individual characteristics to assign them to the appropriate cluster. This method greatly reduces computational load by quickly classifying elements with clear cluster associations, thereby focusing resources on elements with more ambiguous status. Such an approach is particularly advantageous in cloud forensics, where the vast amounts of data make identifying relevant information a challenging and resource-intensive task. The CFMM Algorithm is shown in Figure 4. The CFMM Clustering Algorithm is a methodical process for organizing data specifically for forensic analysis. Required inputs include a dataset labeled dataset to cluster: $X = \{x1, \dots, xn\}$ in R^p . Parameters: c, β, δ, ϕ ensure the cluster decision results. An object is constructed without meta-clusters, containing n entities, each within p dimensions, alongside c, β, δ, ϕ , which guide the clustering. The procedure is twofold. It begins by establishing objects devoid of meta-clusters and updating each object's belief mass through iterative calculations. Based on these beliefs, objects are first sorted as outliers, or as belonging distinctly or ambiguously to clusters. This establishes an initial separation of the data. Subsequently, the method recalculates

meta-cluster centers and modifies the CFMM for a more equitable distribution of belief. It then focuses on the previously ambiguous objects, re-evaluating and reassigning them to the most fitting clusters. The algorithm concludes with a dynamic partition that offers a detailed and nuanced categorization of the data, tailored for forensic applications.

Algorithm 1: CFMM Clustering Algorithm

1. **Require:** Dataset to cluster: $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ in R^p ; Parameters: c, β, δ, ϕ
2. **Ensure:** Cluster decision results
3. **Step 1**
4. Construct the object without meta-clusters using (1)–(2); Iterate the mass of beliefs for each object by (2)–(3);
5. **For**
The 1th to n^{th} query object preliminary assign the object as the outlier, either precise or imprecise using (3);
End
6. **Sub-return:** Preliminary partition.
7. **Step 2** Calculate the centers of meta-cluster using (1);
8. Reconstruct the objective method CFMM for credal redistribution using (3);
9. Reiterate the mass of beliefs for the q imprecise objects using (1), (2);
10. **For** the 1th to q^{th} imprecise object reassign the object to a singleton cluster or meta-cluster.
End
11. **Sub return:** Partial specific redistribution.
12. **Return:** Dynamic partition

Fig. 4. Pseudo code of CFMM.

Fig. 5. CFMM clustering process.

Figure 5 explains the CFMM clustering process, which is divided into 2 major portions to sort and organize the clustered data. The flowchart illustrates a structured method for identifying shared processes and concepts within a dataset collected from 18 different metamodels. Initially, the data are gathered and then segregated into two distinct datasets—one for processes and the other for concepts. These are then methodically sorted and organized. Subsequently, two simultaneous approaches are undertaken to determine the commonalities: an algorithmic approach, which incorporates methods such as the Elbow method, co-clustering, DBSCAN, K-means, Hierarchical, and GMM algorithms, along with a manual approach. The latter involves extracting the most frequently occurring concepts and processes. Following the identification stage, the results procured from both approaches undergo expert validation. The final step involves a comparative analysis of the findings from the algorithmic and manual methods. The culmination of this procedure is the determination of the agreed-upon common processes and concepts, signifying the end of the process. This flowchart depicts a comprehensive approach, melding algorithmic computation with manual scrutiny to validate the outcomes through expert review, ensuring the findings are reliable and accurate.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cloud environments can vary significantly based on the service providers, configurations, and technologies used. Creating a unified metamodel helps standardize the representation of cloud forensic data, ensuring consistency and compatibility across different cloud environments. A unified metamodel enables different tools and systems to exchange and share cloud forensic data seamlessly. Usually, interoperability is crucial for the collaboration between multiple organizations or teams involved in cloud forensic investigations. Cloud forensics often requires data from various sources, such as logs, network traffic, virtual machine snapshots, and configuration data. A unified metamodel allows investigators to integrate and analyze diverse data types more efficiently, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the incident to improve accuracy and NMI. The results of the proposed CFMM are explained below.

A. Artifact-wise Clustering Results

Table III explains the Artifact-wise Clustering Results which are selected from datasets and are the most meaningful in terms of accuracy to NMI. Table IV contains clusters no. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11 from the datasets mentioned in Table I. Figure 6 explains the results of Table III. The Elbow method is utilized to determine the optimal number of clusters in a dataset. The frequency values indicate how often each cluster number was identified as the optimal choice in different iterations. Notably, cluster number 5 emerges as the most frequent optimal choice, being identified 3 times, which suggests it might be the most suitable number of clusters for the dataset. Cluster numbers 4 and 6 also appear as potentially optimal, but less frequent, each with a frequency of 2. In contrast, the rest cluster numbers are considered suboptimal for the given data. Table IV illustrates the selected clusters and compares them with existing approaches in terms of accuracy.

A total of 8 iterations were performed for comparison. We can see how the proposed CFMM approach is significantly more accurate than the existing techniques. Figure 7 exhibits the superb accuracy of the proposed CFMM approach. Figure 7(i) states the overall average % results between the proposed CFMM and existing approaches.

TABLE III. RESULTS OF THE CFMM METHOD

Cluster No.	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Frequency	2	3	2	0	1	0	2	1

Fig. 6. CFMM clustering results.

TABLE IV. RESULT COMPARISON

	K-Means [28]	Hierarchical [24]	DBSCAN [24]	GMM [45]	CFMM
Cluster No 4	0.46	0.56	0.23	0.65	0.96
Cluster No 5	0.7	0.15	0.15	0.24	0.83
Cluster No 6	0.11	0.18	0.2	0.26	0.85
Cluster No 7	0.13	0.16	0.19	0.24	0.73
Cluster No 8	0.15	0.18	0.22	0.24	0.71
Cluster No 9	0.17	0.13	0.25	0.24	0.89
Cluster No 10	0.19	0.11	0.26	0.24	0.79
Cluster No 11	0.21	0.14	0.23	0.19	0.81

Figure 7(a) illustrates the comparison for cluster no 4. Clustering quality metric accuracy is used. It rates the performance on a scale from 0 to 1, where 1 signifies the ideal clustering arrangement. The CFMM algorithm emerges as the most effective, with a near-perfect score of 0.96, indicating its superior ability to cluster the given dataset. The GMM method registers a moderate effectiveness with a score of 0.6. The other algorithms, have a lower clustering performance. The DBSCAN algorithm's performance is not depicted, suggesting a negligible score.

Figure 7(b) compares the same set of algorithms, however, the performance scores vary from Figure 7(a). The proposed CFMM maintains its lead with a score of 0.83, affirming its robustness in effectively clustering the dataset. K-means clustering is still a competitive method, with a score of 0.7, denoting a high level of effectiveness. Conversely, DBSCAN, GMM, and Hierarchical show considerably lower scores, all either at or below 0.26, which implies these methods are less suitable for the dataset based on the metric used. The CFMM algorithm's consistent high performance across both figures indicates its potential as the preferred method for the dataset. For the rest of the cluster numbers mentioned in Figure 7, the accuracy of the proposed approach is always better than that of the compared methods.

Fig. 7. (a) Cluster 4, (b) Cluster 5, (c) Cluster 6, (d) Cluster 7, (e) Cluster 8, (f) Cluster 9, (g) Cluster 10, (h) Cluster 11, (i) overall average ratio.

B. Clustering of Digital Forensics Results

Table IV illustrates the selected cluster results of the proposed CFMM and compares them with the ones of known approaches such as K-Means, Hierarchical, DBSCAN in terms of NMI. A total of 8 iterations have been performed. We can see that the proposed CFMM approach had significantly improved NMI in comparison to the other techniques. Figure 8 shows the result comparison (NMI).

TABLE V. NMI RESULTS OF SELECTED CLUSTERS

Algorithms/ Clusters	K- Means	Hierarchical	DBSCAN	GMM	CFMM
Cluster No 4	0.41	0.51	0.23	0.64	0.91
Cluster No 5	0.62	0.09	0.2	0.38	0.79
Cluster No 6	0.65	0.11	0.22	0.33	0.78
Cluster No 7	0.62	0.09	0.26	0.38	0.79
Cluster No 8	0.58	0.13	0.16	0.31	0.77
Cluster No 9	0.72	0.14	0.31	0.39	0.85
Cluster No 10	0.74	0.16	0.29	0.41	0.88
Cluster No 11	0.75	0.17	0.27	0.43	0.89

Considering the performance scores across the approaches, the average effectiveness of each algorithm can be estimated. CFMM appears to be the most efficient algorithm on average, given its leading scores in both evaluations. K-Means, despite its lower score, shows a moderate average performance, potentially indicating its versatility across different experiment settings. Hierarchical and GMM algorithms present a consistent, though not leading, performance, suggesting their utility in certain

contexts. DBSCAN appears less effective on average, which could be due to its sensitivity to density parameters or the data nature. These averages provide insight into the general applicability of each algorithm, though the specific choice would depend on the particularities of the dataset and the clustering objectives.

Fig. 8. (a) Cluster 4, (b) Cluster 5, (c) Cluster 6, (d) Cluster 7, (e) Cluster 8, (f) Cluster 9, (g) Cluster 10, (h) Cluster 11, (i) overall average ratio.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduced the innovative Cloud Forensic Meta-Model (CFMM), seamlessly integrated with advanced machine learning algorithms, to significantly enhance data collection and analytical capabilities within cloud computing environments. Not only does this approach set a new standard for cloud forensics in terms of data processing and reliability, but also distinctly differentiates itself from the existing theoretical models. A key contribution of our research is the standardization of CFMM processes, which guarantees consistent and precise forensic data analysis across diverse cloud platforms. Furthermore, we outlined the common investigation processes within the CFMM framework, identifying five core stages: pre-preparation, verification, data analysis, collection, and documentation. Our study also effectively categorized and extracted several pivotal concepts from the dataset-CFMM. In addition, this study identified several concepts that were gathered from the dataset-based CFMM. On the other hand, these processes differ and have diverse meanings and synonyms. After that, the frequency feature was employed to choose the most prevalent concepts

for each category. As a result, a total of 5 common concepts were chosen based on machine learning approach and the results were compared with the ones of known approaches. Several concept definitions were reconciled using the CFMM method.

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Elasticity and Load-Displacement Behavior of Engineered Cementitious Composites produced with Different Polymeric Fibers

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ABSTRACT

Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECC) are ultra-ductile materials, and the fibers used provide superior flexibility and strain capacity. This study investigates the use of two different types of polymeric fibers, Polypropylene (PP) and Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA), with volume fractions of 1 and 2%, and studies their effect on stress-strain relationships, load-displacement behavior, toughness, and elasticity of ECC mixes produced with two strength levels, 30 and 60 MPa. The results showed that mixtures with PVA fiber ionic coating had a better performance than those with PP fibers due to the chemical reaction between the PVA fibers and the ECC matrix. This performance was confirmed by Scanning Electronic Microscopy (SEM). For normal-strength concrete (30 MPa), the modulus of elasticity increased by 7.8 and 9.6% for mixes with PP and PVA fibers, respectively, while in high-strength mixes (60 MPa), it increased by 9.4 and 10.85%, respectively. Toughness increases with increasing matrix strength, which is associated with an increase in cement content and fiber fraction. This study also investigates the effect of incorporating a PVA solution in ECC mixes, which leads to an increase in yield stress. This behavior was observed in the stress-strain behavior of 60 MPa mixes with 2% fibers which were compared to 30 MPa mixes with 1% fibers.

Keywords-Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC); Polypropylene (PP) fibers; Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) fibers; polyvinyl alcohol acetate; stress-strain behavior; load-deflection curve; modulus of elasticity

I. INTRODUCTION

Conventional concrete members are unyielding and have a strain capacity of at most 0.1%, producing high-brittleness concrete. The absence of normal concrete bendability is a notable cause of strain failure and is considered a controlling power in creating an elegant material, known as Engineered Cementitious Composite (ECC) concrete [1]. This type of concrete can exhibit intensely improved flexibility [2], as it is reinforced with tiny and disconnected polymer fibers that are micromechanical, specifically designed, and used up to 2% by volume [3]. Thus, ECC concrete deforms without breaking

more than conventional concrete [4]. The formation of ECC concrete relies on the interaction between the matrix and the fibers, which is considered an essential factor for its behavior, as it results in a modification in the interfacial zone and provides an ideal property. Using appropriate mineral admixtures may prevent fiber pull-out from the matrix [3]. ECC concrete with 2% fibers improves tensile strain capacity by 3 to 7%. The diverse constituents of ECC concrete help resisting the subjected load and are 40 times lighter and 50 times more flexible than conventional concrete [4]. Instead of tension-softening, ECC experiences strain-hardening, which means that the material endures higher loads at a progressively

imposed strain on the uniaxially tensioned specimen [4]. The addition of Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) acetate solution improves the durability and bonding strength of cementing materials [5]. PVA solutions are added directly to cement in the form of an aqueous solution to improve the properties of ECC concrete. Many studies have shown that adding a certain amount of PVA can improve the water retention and workability of ECC concrete in the fresh state [6]. Unlike FRC, the rising tensile deformation in ECC is nonlocalized, as it spreads from the first crack to multiple cracks that cover the specimen's volume. Increasing the number of microcracks and controlling the widths of the cracks to not exceed 100 μm increases the tensile ductility. ECC's strain-hardening increases with fiber volume content. Using silica fume with PVA fibers in ECC concrete mixes creates a surface coating that prevents fibers from slipping when loaded without fracturing [4]. According to [3], the increase in compressive strength between ECC concrete mixes made with Portland Limestone Cement (PLC), with and without fibers, was 36.11, 45.5, and 52.4% after 28, 56, and 90 days. In addition, its exceptional energy absorption makes ECC concrete suitable for use in seismic zones or microstructure tailoring [3].

Adding Polypropylene (PP) fibers with adequate tensile strength makes concrete more ductile, since it acts as a bridge at the matrix/fiber interface, making it more durable and robust and improving its bonding strength and microstructure [7]. The high density of high-strength concrete avoids water evaporation, leading to greater strength gain [8-9]. The modulus of elasticity of high-strength concrete reinforced with polymer grids shows greater improvement than normal-strength concrete due to its higher density and the use of high range water-reducing agents, leading to an increase in compressive strength [10]. This study investigates the modulus of elasticity behavior of ECC concrete with two grades of strength, normal (30 MPa) and high (60 MPa), reinforced with 1% and 2% PP and PVA fibers, and containing PVA solution and silica fume. This study also investigates the stress-strain behavior of ECC concrete and detects the load-displacement performance and the toughness of these mixes. SEM was used to identify the microstructural behavior of the engineered cementitious composite. The results of this study may open the horizon beyond the use of such mixes in constructions exposed to tensile stresses without the need to use traditional bar reinforcement.

II. MATERIALS

The ECC concrete used in this study was composed of ordinary Portland cement [11] with two cement content ratios: 275 and 450 kg/m^3 , for 28-day concrete compressive strengths of 30 and 60 MPa, respectively. Fine aggregate (sand) sieve analysis grading confirmed IQS No.45/84, lying in zone II [12]. Silica fume with a strength activity index of 120% [13] was used. Table I shows the characteristics of the PP and PVA fibers. The PVA solution was used to reduce the porosity and enhance the density of ECC. The compressive strength test was performed after 28 days of water-curing, and the cylinders were tested according to [14]. The modulus of elasticity test was applied on a cylinder of 300x150 mm according to [15]. The stress-strain relationship was recorded for 300x150 mm

cylinders at a curing age of 28 days. The test procedure was conducted according to [15]. Each cylinder's top surface was leveled using a diamond-stoned grinder to ensure a smooth and leveled surface. The load-displacement test was performed on a 100x100x400 mm prism in accordance with [16]. Tables II and III present the properties of the four mixes. Mixes of 30 MPa with a 1% volume fraction of fibers and 60 MPa with a 2% volume fraction of fibers were used to investigate modulus of elasticity, stress-strain relationship, toughness, and the load-displacement behavior of ECC-bendable concrete. These fiber ratios were chosen based on their better performance in the mixes to avoid the balling effect that occurs when using high-volume fractions of fibers with poor paste content.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF POLYMERIC FIBERS

Characteristics	PVA	PP
Elongation, %	6	10
Length, mm	12	12
Diameter, μm	0.039	0.032
Color	Light yellow	White
Shape	Straight	Straight
Density, kg/m^3	1300	910
Tensile strength, MPa,	1620	600 - 700
Modulus of elasticity, GPa,	42.8	36

TABLE II. MIX PROPORTIONS BY WEIGHT

Materials	30 MPa	60 MPa
cement	1	1
sand	0.8	0.8
SF [*]	0.1	0.1
SP [*]	0.013	0.02
PVAs [*]	0.01	0.01
w/b [*]	0.42	0.3

*SP: superplasticizer percentage, *SF: silica fume percentage, *PVAs: polyvinyl alcohol solution, *w/b: water to binder ratio

TABLE III. DETAILS OF THE USED MIXES

Mix Designation	28-days compressive strength (MPa)	Fiber type	Fiber (%)
30P	30	PP	1
30V	30	PVA	1
60P	60	PP	2
60V	60	PVa	2

III. TEST METHOD AND STANDARDS

A. Modulus of Elasticity

A concrete cylinder of 150 mm diameter and 300 mm height was tested according to [17], to investigate the modulus of elasticity. The average modulus of elasticity of three specimens was calculated after 28, 60, and 90 days.

B. Stress-Strain Relationship

The stress-strain behavior of ECC concrete using PVA and PP fibers with two volume fractions, 1% for 30 MPa and 2% for 60 MPa, was investigated for an age of 28 days.

C. Load-Displacement Test

The load-displacement test was performed using the third-point bending test on an ECC concrete beam of 100x100x400 mm, with a span length of 300 mm. The test procedure was

determined according to [16]. Four mixes were detected for the load-deflection behavior, as described in Table III.

D. Field Emission–Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM)

This test is used to inspect various materials and characterize their structure and composition, as it provides a stable, high-resolution platform that can meet most research needs from a collection of accurate and fast data: images of surface and composition can be combined with fast elemental analysis to determine the properties and the elemental composition of the material. This study used the FE-SEM test to determine the bond behavior between the PP and PVA polymeric fibers and the matrix, which has a great influence on the mechanical behavior of the ECC concrete mixes.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Strength and Elasticity

The compressive strength and modulus of elasticity test results in Table IV show that fiber type does not have a significant effect on compressive strength. Figure 1 shows that using PVA fiber for normal-strength concrete gives a higher modulus of elasticity than using PP. This behavior is attributed to the high tensile strength of PVA, which is 1620 MPa compared to the 700 MPa for PP. In addition, the higher modulus of elasticity of PVA fibers, reflects its effect on the modulus of elasticity of the ECC mixes. For normal-strength concrete, the increase in modulus of elasticity was 7.8 and 9.6% for mixes with PP and PVA fibers, respectively. For high-strength concrete, the increase in modulus of elasticity was 9.4 and 10.85% for mixes with PP and PVA fibers, respectively. For normal strength mixes, the increase in modulus of elasticity when using PVA compared to PP fibers was approximately 2.4% after 90 days. Furthermore, for high-strength concrete mixes after 90 days, the use of PVA fibers showed a 3.3% increase in modulus of elasticity compared to PP.

Figure 2 shows the error bars of the standard deviation of the modulus of elasticity for different fiber content and strength levels. The bar charts represent the average modulus of elasticity for each mix at 28, 60, and 90 days. There is an overlap between error bars in mixtures of the same strength, indicating that there are no huge differences in the modulus of elasticity for different fiber types. Also, it can be noticed that there is no overlap in the error bars between different mixes, indicating that there are obvious differences when using different fiber content and types. Mixes of 60 MPa with 2% PVA fibers recorded the highest modulus of elasticity over time, due to the high density, good fiber distribution, high cement content, high tensile strength of PVA fibers, high fiber content, and adequate chemical and mechanical bond between PVA fibers and matrix.

TABLE IV. TEST RESULTS OF CONCRETE MIXES

Age (days)	Compressive strength (MPa)			Modulus of elasticity (GPa)		
	28	60	90	28	60	90
30P	32	34	37	23	23.86	24.8
30V	34	36.4	38.7	24	24.6	26.3
60P	61.53	62	65.49	30.1	30.5	32.94
60V	62.79	63.23	69	30.67	31.27	34

Fig. 1. The relationship of modulus of elasticity with age for the mixes.

Fig. 2. Error bars for standard deviation for modulus of elasticity with age for different concrete mixes.

Figures 3 and 4 show the relationship between the compressive strength and the modulus of the elasticity of normal-strength concrete. The modulus of elasticity had low variation in normal-strength concrete despite using different fiber types.

Fig. 3. Relationship between the modulus of elasticity and compressive strength for normal-strength concrete produced with PP fibers.

Fig. 4. Relationship between the modulus of elasticity and compressive strength for normal-strength concrete produced with PVA fibers.

Figures 5 and 6 show that in high-strength concrete, the mixes produced with PVA fibers had a greater increase in modulus of elasticity than the mixes made with PP. This performance may be due to the higher modulus of elasticity of PVA (42.8 GPa) compared to PP fibers (36 GPa) and the higher cement content for 60 MPa mixes, which provides better bonding with the fibers and better fiber distributions. The equations shown in Figures 3-6 have a high determination coefficient (R^2), which assures their suitability to predict the modulus of elasticity for each mix from its compressive strength. These equations were compared to the ACI 318 [18] and ACI 363 [19] equations:

$$ACI\ 318: E_c = 4700 \times \sqrt{f'c} \quad (1)$$

$$ACI\ 363\ (Martines): E_c = 3320 \times \sqrt{f'c} + 6900 \quad (2)$$

$$ACI\ 363\ (Radain): E_c = 14495 + 2176 \times \sqrt{f'c} \quad (3)$$

$$ACI\ 363\ (NS\ 3473): E_c = 9500 \times (f'c)^{0.3} \quad (4)$$

Table V shows the relationships between the modulus of elasticity and compressive strength. The estimated results were compared to the results from the ACI equations, showing convergence with a variation between the ACI and the actual equation results of about 17, 14.5, 9, and 7.2% for mixes 30PP, 30V, 60PP, and 60V, respectively.

TABLE V. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE ACTUAL RESULTS AND THE ACI RESULTS

	30 PP			30 V			60 PP			60 V		
	28 days	60 days	90 days	28 days	60 days	90 days	28 days	60 days	90 days	28 days	60 days	90 days
Compressive strength	32	34	37	34.5	36.4	38.7	61.53	62	65.49	62.79	63.23	69
Actual E_c	23	23.86	24.8	24	24.6	26.3	30.1	30.5	31.49	30.67	31.27	33
(1)	26.5	27.4	28.5	27.6	28.3	29.2	36.8	37	38	37.2	37.4	39
(2)	25.6	26.3	27	26.4	26.9	27.55	32.9	33	33.76	33.2	33.299	34.477
(3)	26.8	27.18	27.7	27.276	27.6	28	31.56	31.63	32	31.737	31.797	32.57
(4)	26.87	27.36	28	27.48	27.93	28.45	32.69	32.767	33.31	32.89	32.96	33.83

B. Stress-Strain Relationship

Figures 7-10 show the stress-strain behavior of ECC at the age of 28 days. The strain change reflects the matrix toughness and the interaction of the fiber/matrix properties [4].

Fig. 7. Stress-strain curve for normal strength concrete reinforced with 1% PP fibers.

The stress-strain behavior for mix 30V is attributed to the ionic coating properties of the PVA fibers and the chemical interaction with the cement matrix that restricts concrete flaws and microcrack propagation. The same explanation also can be

Fig. 5. Relationship between the modulus of elasticity and compressive strength for high-strength concrete produced with PP fibers.

Fig. 6. Relationship between the modulus of elasticity and compressive strength for high-strength concrete produced with PVA fibers.

applied to the high-strength mixes in Figures 9-10. The elasticity of the mix is affected by the used fiber volume fraction and type. Therefore, it can be noticed that mixes with PVA fibers have higher elastic behavior than mixes with PP fibers. Also, mixes with 2% fiber content show a higher elastic trend than mixes with 1% fiber.

Fig. 8. Stress-strain curve for normal strength concrete reinforced with 1% PVA fibers.

Fig. 9. Stress-strain curve for high-strength concrete reinforced with 2% PP fibers.

Fig. 10. Stress-strain curve for high-strength concrete reinforced with 2% PVA fibers.

C. Load-Displacement Relationship

Figures 11 and 12 show the flexural responses of PP and PVA ECC cement under loading. These figures show a deflection hardening behavior, indicating that the load grows even after the initiation of the crack in the matrix.

The load-displacement curve of high-strength ECC concrete mixes indicates that the distributed tensile deformation causes the spread of a strain in the compressive zone of the beam. In ordinary concrete mixes, concentrating strain in the compressive zone of the beam leads to brittle spalling [4]. The key differences in ECC's elasticity and load-displacement behavior produced with PP and PVA fibers are that PVA improves the elasticity behavior of the ECC mixes and increases their capacity to bear the applied load, compared to PP which gives the same enhancement in an inferior degree.

Fig. 11. Load-displacement curve for normal-strength concrete with PVA and PP fibers.

Fig. 12. Load-displacement curve for high-strength concrete with PVA and PP fibers.

D. Toughness

Table VI shows the areas under the load-displacement curves, which are defined as the ECC concrete toughness.

TABLE VI. TOUGHNESS OF THE ECC CONCRETE MIXES

Mixes	Toughness (J/m ³)
30P	856
60P	2095
30V	958
60V	2880

The toughness of the ECC matrix is ruled by its ingredients. When the maximum energy exceeds the matrix toughness, crack propagation is achieved after the crack starts from a defective site [4]. This can be realized by restricting the matrix toughness, which can be achieved by varying the matrix ingredients. Table VI shows that as the strength of the matrix increases, which is related to an increase in cement and fiber content, the toughness of the mixes increases. For normal-strength concrete, the toughness of the 30V mixes was about 12% higher than that of the 30P mixes. The same behavior can be observed in 60V mixes compared to 60P mixes, where the toughness increase was 37%. This behavior may be related to the increase in fiber content in high-strength mixes. The degree of ductility depends on the fiber type and is directly proportional to the fiber content. This explanation agrees with [20], which concluded that the higher fiber content in FRC leads to a lower corresponding post-crack load drop.

E. Field Emission-Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM)

SEM analysis is characterized by easy sampling, a variety of accessible knowledge, and good resolution [21]. PVA fibers provided better behavior than PP fibers in the ECC, because of the chemical bond between their ionic coating and the cement matrix. Figure 13 represents the bond area between the PVA fibers and the cement matrix for 500x(200 μm) magnification. Figure 14 represents the bond situation between the PP fibers and the cement matrix for 600x magnification. In general, adding polymeric fibers to concrete mixes leads to a remarkable improvement in its behavior, especially its flexural strength, which is consistent with the conclusions of [22].

V. CONCLUSIONS

1. Engineered high-strength (60 MPa) cementitious composite concrete containing 2% PVA fibers showed the highest results in modulus of elasticity, and its load-displacement curves showed higher yield stress levels.

Fig. 13. The bond between PVA fibers and the matrix.

Fig. 14. The bond between polypropylene fibers and concrete matrix.

2. The presence of a PVA solution provides good cohesion strength, and the presence of polymeric fibers, having adequate tensile strength, makes the engineered cementitious composite concrete more ductile.
3. The elasticity of the mixture is affected by the type and fraction of fibers used. Therefore, it can be noticed that ECC mixes with PVA fibers had a higher elastic behavior than mixes with PP. In addition, mixes with 2% fiber content showed a higher elastic trend than mixes with 1% fiber.
4. The higher modulus of elasticity of PVA fibers compared to PP reflects its effect on the modulus of elasticity of the ECC mixes.
5. The flexural responses of PP and PVA ECC concrete under loading show deflection hardening behavior.
6. The toughness of the ECC matrix is ruled by its material components and the matrix strength, which is related to an increase in cement content and fiber volume fraction.

Therefore, the matrix toughness increases as the strength and fiber content increase.

7. For normal-strength concrete (30 MPa), mixes containing PVA fibers exhibit an increase of approximately 12% in comparison with the mixes containing PP fibers. The same behavior can be observed for high-strength concrete (60 MPa), where mixes containing PVA fibers showed an increase in toughness of approximately 37% higher than ECC concrete mixes containing PP fibers.
8. The superior behavior of PVA fibers is related to their higher modulus of elasticity and their ionic coating, which provides good chemical bonding with the cement matrix, leading to an increase in the toughness and elasticity behavior of the ECC concrete mixes.
9. SEM revealed the bond behavior between the polymeric fibers and the ECC concrete matrix.
10. SEM showed that microcracks below 50 μm were controlled by polymeric fibers and the sequence of developing microcracks leads to an improved strain capacity of the ECC mixes.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data will be made available on request.

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The Effect of Opening Size and Expansion Ratio on the Flexural Behavior of Hot Rolled Wide Flange Steel Beams with Expanded Web

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ABSTRACT

In some design cases, such as in castellated beams, cellular beams, or steel beams with expanded web, it is advantageous to strengthen and enhance the performance of steel beams by increasing the web depth. However, expanding the web of a steel beam is a unique engineering strategy. This modification not only enhances its ability to bear heavy loads but also reduces any bending or flexing while enabling longer distances between supports. The expanded steel beams can be achieved by making a horizontal cutting in the steel beam web and then adding an increment plate (with the same web thickness), called spacer plate, between the two halves of the web sections, thus improving stiffness and strength. To evaluate the behavior of such beams, nine specimens of HEA steel beams with expanded web ratios of 150%, 200%, and 250%, and one specimen as a reference beam, were fabricated. The specimens were evaluated under two-point load over a clear span length of 280 cm. From the experimental work it was found that for steel beams with expanded web that have 18 openings with 80 mm, the beams with an expansion ratio of 150% had the best performance according to load-deflection behavior with a reduction in load capacity by only 11%. Additionally, the beams with expansion ratios of 200% and 250% had no economic viability according to the analysis of load-deflection behavior with a reduction in load capacity by 49% and 62%, compared with the solid expanded steel beam with the same expansion ratio. For the second type of steel beam with expanding web with 9 openings of 160 mm width, the beams with expansion ratios of 200% and 250% were observed to perform better than the first type with a reduction in load capacity by 28% and 50%. Using larger opening width and a smaller opening number is considered the best option for beams with expansion web ratios of 200% and 250%, while on the contrary, using smaller opening width and higher numbers seems to be a better option for beams with 150% expansion web ratio. Expanding the depth of a steel beam provides design flexibility, reduces deflections, and allows for longer spans. These benefits enhance material efficiency and open up new architectural possibilities.

Keywords-expansion ratio; Vierendeel mechanisms; web post-buckling; web opening ratio

I. INTRODUCTION

Large-scale steel structural projects like parking structures, supermarkets, and storage facilities have frequently used beams with expanded web depth. Expanding the web of a steel beam is a unique engineering strategy to enhance the strength and overall performance of structures. Not only does this modification ameliorate its ability to bear heavy loads, but also reduces bending or flexing while enabling longer distances between supports compared to the original section [1, 2]. In some design cases, it is advantageous to strengthen the steel beams by increasing the web depth, e.g. in castellated beams, cellular beams, or expanded steel beams [2]. However, the presence of an opening in steel beams affects beam stiffness

and causes an increase in the deflection, decreases the beam capacity, and increase the stress at the corners of the opening [3]. Castellated beams and cellular beams are steel (I or H) section members with square, rectangular, circular, or hexagonal shape openings, positioned at regular intervals along the web [5]. Compared to solid beams, beams with openings offer advantages such as weight reduction and functional versatility but may experience reduced strength and stiffness, as well as potential serviceability challenges. Selecting the proper beam type depends on specific application requirements and design considerations. The utilization of steel beams with web openings presents numerous advantages when compared to classical I-section elements in modern construction. These benefits encompass improved architectural appearance, a

superior strength-to-weight ratio, and the seamless integration of utilities, such as pipes, ducts, or electrical conduits without any compromise to the beam's structural integrity. This innovative design facilitates efficient space utilization and simplifies the installation process, making it a favored option for constructing large span structures, including multi-story buildings, bridges, and stadiums [4]. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the presence of openings in expanded steel beams leads to a reduction in shear capacity and altering failure modes. In contrast, the steel beam openings decrease the stiffness of beams and hence result in larger deflection, which introduces more complex design considerations. The fabrication costs of expanded steel girders are higher compared to regular plain webbed beams. However, these additional costs can be offset using materials that are more economical. Moreover, residual stresses are introduced within steel beams with openings, which can affect their structural behavior. These stresses contribute to a decrease in the critical buckling load and must be considered during the design process. Many studies investigated the effect of multiple web openings along the span length of RC beams [5-8].

The use of expanded steel beams has become more popular in the last two decades and it is controlled by well-established design rules and practice codes, which are updated on a regular basis to reflect new results and advancements. [9-11]. Unlike castellated beams or cellular beams, the expanded steel beams are constructed by making a horizontal cutting in the steel beam web and then adding an increment plate called spacer plate (with the same web thickness) between the two halves of the web sections. The new member can be created with or without openings. This method improves the stiffness and strength of the steel beam [12]. It is important to note that the design and installation of increment plates should be done in accordance with engineering standards and guidelines. Consulting with a structural engineer or a professional in the field of steel construction is recommended to ensure proper design and implementation for a safe and effective expansion of the steel web [13 12]. It has been stated that, beams with openings can be used to replace solid beams with the same requirements if stiffeners are provided in the right number, size, and location. Furthermore, it has been noted that the existence of web openings in steel beams can lead to reduced weight and increased structural efficiency [15, 16]. Yet, there is a lack in literature regarding the behavior of steel beams with expanded web with horizontal cutting patterns. Accordingly, in this paper, the behavior of expanded steel beams with horizontal cutting patterns is examined. Different expanding ratios and opening details will be investigated.

II. THE EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A. HEA Steel Beam

Hot rolled standard steel (HE160A) was used in this study to fabricate the steel beams with expanded web. Its characteristics can be seen in Tables I-II.

B. Plates

To implement the strengthening technique, plates were employed as stiffeners. Their characteristics can be observed in Table III.

TABLE I. HEA BEAM (160A) SECTION CHARACTERISTICS

Parameter	G	h	tf	tw	A	r	I	Sx	Zx
Unit	kg/m	mm	mm	mm	mm ²	mm	mm ⁴	mm ³	mm ³
Value	30.4	152	9	6	38.8	15	167	220	245

TABLE II. HEA BEAM MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Property	Ultimate yield strength	Ultimate tensile strength	Modulus of elasticity	Elongation percentage
Unit	MPa	MPa	MPa	%
Value	322	459	210000	22

TABLE III. PLATE MECHANICAL AND SECTION CHARACTERISTICS

Property	Thickness	Yield stress	Ultimate stress	Elongation
Unit	mm	MPa	MPa	%
Value	5.9	253	482	30

C. Tested Specimens

Nine specimens were fabricated as HEA steel beams with an expanded web and one specimen as a reference beam. The specimens were tested under two-point load over a clear span length of 280 cm and a total length of 300 cm. The fabricated samples' details are explained in Figures 1-5 and Table IV.

Fig. 1. Dimensions of beams RB01 and RB02.

Fig. 2. Dimensions of beams RB03 and RB04.

D. Manufacturing of Steel Beams with Expanded Web

In the experimental work and in order to produce the steel beams with expanded web specimens, the web section was linearly cut in a horizontal pattern along their centerline using a numerical control (CNC) plasma-cutting machine. Then the two halves were separated as shown in Figure 6. In order to produce a solid expanded web, an increment plate was added between the two web halves that have been cut horizontally

(the plate had the same beam length and thickness with the beam web), then welding was used to join the plate and the two web halves together to create a new expanded beam. In addition, for producing steel beam with expanded web specimen contain openings, increment plates with specific dimensions in regular intervals were adopted. Vertical bearing stiffeners were welded to the web at concentrated point loads, and at ends (above supports) as illustrated in Figure 7. The plates above the supports are 200 mm wide and the plates under loads are 100 mm wide in all specimens with openings. In all beam specimens, proper sequence of welding was adopted since distortion would take place with two welders employed and the welding was conducted from the center outwards to the ends [17].

TABLE IV. DETAILS OF STEEL BEAM SPECIMENS (mm)

Se. No.	<i>h</i> (mm)	Expansion ratio %	Opening ratio %	Opening height (mm)	Opening width (mm)	No. of openings
RB01	152	NA	0	NA	NA	0
RB02	228	150	0	NA	NA	0
RB03	304	200	0	NA	NA	0
RB04	380	250	0	NA	NA	0
G2B1	228	150	48	76	80	18
G2B2	228	150	48	76	160	9
G3B1	304	200	48	152	80	18
G3B2	305	200	48	152	160	9
G4B1	380	250	48	228	80	18
G4B2	380	250	48	228	160	9

Fig. 3. Dimensions of beams G2B1 and G2B2.

Fig. 4. Dimensions of beams G3B1 and G3B2.

Fig. 5. Dimensions of beams G4B1 and G4B2.

Fig. 6. Fabrication of expanded steel beam web with openings.

E. Test Setup

The beams were subjected to testing in the Structure Laboratory of the Civil Engineering Department of Baghdad University. The testing procedure consisted of applying static top-loading utilizing a hydraulic jack and a load cell with a capacity of 200 tons. The load was incrementally increased, with approximately 500 kg added each time, until the beams reached the point of failure. During the testing process, multiple measurements were taken, including deflections at the center of the beams and strains. Each beam was loaded with two concentrated loads, each load located 450mm away from the beam span center [17, 18].

III. TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All beams were tested engaging a universal testing machine. All specimens were tested under the same loading conditions. The tested specimens were compared with the control specimen. The deflection Serviceability Limit $L/240$ with 12 mm value was used.

A. Load-Deflection Curves

1) Expansion Web Ratio Effect on Solid HEA Beams

The behavior of steel beams is generally assessed based on their strength and their elastic deformations [19]. The influences of increasing web depth by 150%, 200%, and 250% of the original HEA beam web on the load-deflection behavior of solid steel beams with expanded web are shown in Figure 8. The yield point determining procedure is explained in detail in [20].

2) Ultimate Load

It was observed that with the adoption of a steel plate to increase the web depth, the ultimate capacity of carrying loads of beams RB02, RB03, and RB04 increased by 61%, 124%, and 207% with an expanded ratio of 150%, 200%, and 250%, respectively, compared to the reference solid beam RB01. At the deflection service point (12 mm), the carrying loads of beams RB02, RB03, and RB04 increased by 108%, 201%, and 310%, respectively.

3) Deflection

The mid-span deflection at ultimate load of beams RB02, RB03, and RB04 compared with the reference beam RB01 decreased by 16.67%, 57.25%, and 66.67%, respectively. The mid-span deflection at the yield point decreased by 43.75%, 51.25%, and 61.25%. It was thus concluded that as the web expanding ratio increases, the ultimate load increases and the deflection decreases. It should be noted that there is greater influence of expanding web at the deflection service point (12 mm), compared to the ultimate carrying load, and there is greater influence on the deflection at the yield point compared to the mid-deflection at ultimate load. However, it is worth mentioning that increasing the web height can also lead to an increase in weight, because a deeper web requires more material, which can impact the overall weight and cost of the beam. Engineers and designers need to carefully consider the trade-off between increased load-carrying capacity and stiffness versus the potential increase in weight and cost when selecting the expanding web height ratio of a steel beam.

Fig. 7. Load-mid-span deflection curves of beams RB01-RB04.

4) Expanded Web Ratio Effect on Steel Beams with Openings

The influence of the increased (by 150%, 200%, and 250%) web depth of steel beams with the adoption of web openings on the load-deflection behavior is shown in Figures 8-9. The related beams are divided into two categories according to steel web opening width and number. The first type (B1) had a smaller opening width and higher hole numbers whereas the second type (B2) had larger opening width and smaller hole number.

Fig. 8. Load-mid-span deflection curves of beams RB01, G2B1, G3B1, and G4B1.

Fig. 9. Load-mid-span deflection curves of beams (RB01, G2B2, G3B2, and G4B2).

5) Ultimate Load

For the first type (B1): It was noticed that with the adoption of a steel plate to increase the web depth of HEA beams with openings, the ultimate capacity of carrying loads increased by 43%, 13%, and 16% for beams G2B1, G3B1, and G4B1 compared to the reference solid beam RB01. At the deflection service point, the carrying loads of beams G2B1, G3B1, and G4B1 increased by 13.84%, 8.60%, and 17.76%.

For the second type (B2): It was observed that with the adoption of a steel plate to increase the web depth of HEA beams with openings, the ultimate capacity of carrying loads increased by 37%, 60%, and 52% for beams G2B2, G3B2, and G4B2 compared to the reference solid beam RB01. At the deflection service point, the carrying loads of beams G2B2, G3B2, and G4B2 were increased by 30.84%, 77.94%, and 89.72%.

6) Deflection

For the first type (B1): the mid-span deflection at ultimate load of beams G2B1, G3B1, and G4B1 was increased by 112.32%, 47.10%, and 31.52% compared to the reference beam (RB01). The mid-span deflection at the yield point was increased by 43.75%, and 12.50%, respectively.

For the second type (B2): The mid-span deflection at ultimate load of G2B2, and G3B2 was increased by 126.81%,

and 21.01% and that of beam G4B2 was decreased by 44.20% compared to the reference beam (RB01). Additionally, the mid-span deflection at the yield point for beam G2B2 increased by 37.50% and decreased by 25.00% and 46.88% for beams G3B2 and G4B2).

From the above, it was concluded that the expansion of the web with openings can cause an increase in the ultimate load. This improvement in flexural capacity is related to the enhancement in the section stiffness after the expansion process. However, the expansion ratio effect for a solid steel beam with expanded web is noted to be higher than its effect on steel beams with expanded web that has openings, due to the presence of the holes in the web that weaken the overall structural integrity of the steel beam. The web is responsible for carrying shear forces, and any holes can reduce its ability to resist these forces, potentially leading to structural failure. The presence of holes creates stress concentrations, which can result in localized failure and a decrease in the overall strength of the beam, so the presence of holes weakens the web, making it more prone to buckling under compressive loads. It can be stated that, in contrast to solid steel beams with expanded web, the web openings with expanding web influence the carrying load at the deflection service point and yield deflection. Opening width and hole number can have a great impact on the expansion web ratio, influencing the performance of steel beams with openings.

B. General Observations

For the first type, with 80 mm opening width and 18 holes, the beam with an expansion ratio of 150%, had the best performance according to the load-deflection behavior, demonstrating a reduction in load capacity by only 11% compared to a solid expanded steel beam with the same expansion ratio. The beams with expansion ratios of 200%, and 250%, had no economic viability according to the analysis of load-deflection behavior with a reduction in load capacity of 49% and 62%.

For the second type, with 160 mm opening width and 9 holes, the beams with expansion ratios of 200% and 250%, performed better than the first type according to the load-deflection behavior, showcasing a reduction in load capacity of 28%, and 50% compared to the solid expanded steel beam with the same expansion ratio. The beam with expansion ratio of 150% had a reduction in load capacity of 15% compared to the solid expanded steel beam with the same expansion ratio.

The difference between the first type (B1) and the second type (B2) is the web post area divergence that influences web post-buckling. Finally, it can be concluded that using larger opening width and smaller hole number is regarded the best option for beams with expansion web ratios of 200% and 250%. On the contrary, using smaller opening width and higher hole number is the best option for beams with expansion web ratio of 150%. Increasing the web depth in a steel beam improves structural performance, offering design flexibility, reduced deflections, and longer spans, thus enhancing material efficiency and architectural possibilities. However, challenges like construction logistics and potential cost implications should be carefully managed.

C. Modes of Failure

In specimens RB01, RB02, RB03, and RB04 made from solid steel beams (reference non-expanded beam and expanded web), plastic flexural deformation is observed, as depicted in Figures 10-13.

Fig. 10. Mode of failure for beam RB01.

Fig. 11. Mode of failure for beam RB02.

Fig. 12. Mode of failure for beam RB03.

Fig. 13. Mode of failure for beam RB04.

Furthermore, for solid steel beams with expanded web ratios of 0% and 150%, only flexural failure was observed. Yet, for solid steel beams with expanded web ratios of 200 and 250%, both flexure failure and local failure at the stiffeners were spotted.

Fig. 14. Mode of failure for beam G1B1.

In specimens G1B1 and G1B2, made from steel beams with an expanded web ratio of 150%, opening ratio of 30%, opening ratio widths of 30, and 60 mm, and 24 and 12 holes, flexure failure and local failure at the stiffeners were observed, as shown in Figures 14-15.

In specimens G2B1, and G2B2 made from a steel beam with an expanded web ratio of 150%, opening ratio of 60%, opening width of 80 mm, and 18 openings, Vierendeel mechanism was observed. However, with an opening width of 160 mm and 9 holes, Vierendeel mechanism and web weld fracture were detected while a tear in the corner of the openings was also noted, as presented in Figures 16-17.

Fig. 15. Mode of failure for beam G1B2.

Fig. 16. Mode of failure for beam G2B1.

Fig. 17. Mode of failure for beam G2B2.

In specimens G3B1 and G3B2 made from steel beams with an expanded web ratio of 200%, opening ratio of 60%, opening width of 80 mm, and 18 openings, web post-buckling and rapture at the weld line were pinpointed. For the beam with an opening width of 160 mm and 9 holes, web post-buckling was detected, as displayed in Figures 18-19.

In specimens G4B1 and G4B2 made from steel beams with an expanded web ratio of 250%, opening ratio of 60%, opening widths of 80 and 160 mm and 18 and 9 holes, web post buckling was observed, as illustrated in Figures 21 and 22.

Fig. 18. Mode of failure for beam G3B1.

Fig. 19. Mode of failure for beam G3B2.

Fig. 20. Mode of failure for beam G4B1.

Fig. 21. Mode of failure for beam G4B2.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the outcomes of the experimental research, the following conclusions were drawn:

- There is greater influence when expanding the web of steel beams at the deflection service point (12 mm), compared to the ultimate carrying load, and there is greater influence on deflection at the yield point compared to the mid-deflection at the ultimate load.
- For steel beams with expanded web that have 18 openings of 80 mm, the beam with an expansion ratio of 150%, has the best performance according to the load-deflection behavior with a reduction in load capacity by only 11%, whereas the beams with expansion ratios of 200% and 250% have no economic viability.
- For the second type with 9 openings of 160 mm width, the beams with expansion ratios of 200%, and 250%, perform better than the first type according to the load-deflection behavior with a reduction in load capacity of 28% and 50%, and the beam with the expansion ratio of 150% presents a reduction in load capacity of 15%.
- As a conclusion, using larger opening width and a smaller hole number is considered the best option for beams with expansion web ratios of 200% and 250, while utilizing smaller opening width and higher hole number is the best option for beams with expansion web ratio of 150%.
- Expanding the depth of a steel beam has many advantages considering its structural performance. It provides design flexibility, reduces deflections and allows for longer spans. These benefits enhance material efficiency and open up new architectural possibilities including higher material and manufacturing costs, increased weight, connection challenges, space constraints, buckling concerns, serviceability issues, fabrication complexities, and potential unavailability of specialized sections. Careful consideration of project requirements and trade-offs is crucial for optimal design.

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The Potential of Landsat 8 OLI Images in Coastline Identification: The Case Study of Basra, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

Coastline extraction plays important functions in coastal resource management, natural resource preservation, and sustainable coastal development. Long-term records of Landsat data series are available for free downloading, being highly potential for coastline extraction. Furthermore, remote sensing imagery systems along with the application of digital image processing techniques can be utilized in coastline extraction. However, it is challenging to accurately extract coastlines with coarse spatial resolution due to the dynamic properties of various types of coastlines produced by sea-level changes from tides and storms. Moreover, the use of conventional surveys and the need for high-resolution images involve substantial costs and efforts, especially when coastlines of long distances are involved. The current study compared the accuracy of extracting coastlines from Landsat 8 OLI with the observed coastlines from GPS data. In particular, this study focused on distinguishing water areas from non-water areas on the coastline of a selected concrete port. The analysis involved the use of both MNDWI and NDWI indexes. The statistical results demonstrated the accuracy of MNDWI (RMSE of 2.363) and NDWI (RMSE of 2.491 m), which suggested the potential of using Landsat 8 OLI in coastline identification.

Keywords-coastline extraction; Landsat 8 OLI; remote sensing

I. INTRODUCTION

Unlike most ocean-sensing equipment, the Landsat 8 satellite displays higher spatial resolution and sensitivity to color and illumination, providing highly accurate images. More importantly, the images can be generated at wavelengths that allow the identification of deformation caused by the atmosphere, especially when coastal areas are involved. Landsat 8 consists of two sensors, namely an Operational Land Imager (OLI) and a Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS). The data gathered are readily available for free download via GloVis, Earth Explorer, and Landsat Look Viewer [1].

Coastal areas are subjected to threats caused by human activities and natural phenomena, such as coastal erosion-accretion and sea-level changes. Authors in [2-4] argued the importance of representing the coastline and identifying adverse human activities for the sustainability of coastal communities. Despite the beneficial use of conventional ground surveys in creating coastline maps [4], the

incorporation of grounding survey data and images into coastal maps takes up too much time and can be rather costly [4, 5]. Meanwhile, remote sensing is often used to map coastlines and detect related changes due to its macroscopic, real-time, dynamic, and cost-effective features, as well as its broad range of spatial and temporal scales [4, 6, 7]. For instance, authors in [8, 9] utilized the simulated degraded Landsat images in a smooth classification approach for the collection of sub-pixel-scale shorelines, with a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 2.25 m. Authors in [10] suggested the utilization of Landsat TM and ETM+ for the extraction of sub-pixel-scale shorelines, with RMSE ranging from 4.69 m to 5.47 m. Authors in [11] utilized Landsat MSS and TM MS images to monitor the Chinese coastline, which revealed a statistically significant Mean Net Shoreline Movement (MNSM) of 2.54 m and a Mean Absolute Difference (MAD) of 11.26 m. Meanwhile, authors in [12, 13] utilized Landsat images to observe the annual mean shoreline positions with the goal of reducing the short-term variability of shorelines. The study observed that the

retrieved shorelines were biased seaward by 4 m to 5 m, which was attributed to the shift of the natural beaches over time.

The current study focuses on the effective statistical evaluation of determining the error in coastline extraction through the use of Landsat 8 OLI, which would help researchers and practitioners in data construction and analysis.

Fig. 1. Case study.

II. STUDY AREA AND DATA

A. Study Area

In this study, data from Landsat 8 OLI were collected on 12 December 2022. The retrieved data represented Basra City in southern Iraq, which officially divides Kuwait and Iran. Basra is the only Iraqi harbour with a view of the Gulf, which stretches for approximately 60 km. Its strategic location and booming oil industry establish the city as a prime destination for international businesses. In addition, the majority of the residents in Basra reside in areas with easy access to water [14]. The recent economic growth of the city has contributed to substantial interest in topographic data, which are particularly crucial for future building projects that require more precise elevation. However, there are limited topographic data for Basra city, which are mainly confined to a few locations within the city. Referring to Figure 1, it is evident that little is known about the topography of the city center and its surrounding neighborhoods, such as Faro, Quran, and Abu Al-Khasab.

B. Landsat 8 OLI

Landsat data series are typically considered when it comes to coastline extraction due to their ease-of-access feature and extensive history of data collection and revisit coverage. As for the current study, one Landsat 8 OLI multispectral (MS) image, which covers an area of 185×180 km along the track, and one PAN image, which covers the same area for coastline extraction, were acquired. As of 29 December 2022 at 16:03

(UTC), the original Landsat 8 OLI image from path 165 and row 039 was downloaded as a land surface reflectance product in GeoTIFF format from Earth Explore (<http://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>). Landsat 8 OLI images were acquired from the World Geodetic System (WGS84) data. Meanwhile, the final product involved the use of UTM projection. The details of OLI images from Landsat 8 are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I. PROPERTIES AND APPLICATIONS OF LANDSAT 8 BANDS [11]

Landsat 8 Sensors	Band	Wavelength (μm)	Name of the Band	Resolution (m)
OLI	1	0.433 – 0.453	Coastal/Aerosol	30
	2	0.450 – 0.515	Blue	
	3	0.525 – 0.600	Green	
	4	0.630 – 0.680	Red	
	5	0.845 – 0.885	Near-infrared (NIR)	
	6	1.560 – 1.660	Short-wave infrared (SWIR) 1	
	7	2.100 – 2.300	SWIR 2	15
	8	0.500 – 0.680	Panchromatic	
	9	1.360 – 1.390	Cirrus	
TIRS	10	10.30 – 11.30	Long-wave infrared (LWIR) 1	100*
	11	11.50 – 12.50	LWIR 2	
	BQA		Quality Assessment	

*TIRS bands were originally acquired at a resolution of 100 m, but this was reduced to 30 m in the final data product.

C. GPS Data

When it comes to the Global Positioning System (GPS), numerous observation methods are available for use. As for the current study, the rapid static relative positioning and Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) methods were selected to observe all points due to their accuracy and the shorter time required for observation [15, 16]. Rapid static relative positioning and kinematic survey methods are distinctly different in terms of duration. The results from one epoch can potentially be used to determine the location of a roving receiver in a kinematic survey. An epoch rate of 1 s is typically employed for a kinematic survey. The accuracy of intermediate points is within the range of $\pm 1-2$ cm + 2 ppm. The rapid static relative positioning method records $\pm 3-5$ mm + 1 ppm and requires 10 min + 1 min/km, whereas the RTK method has the capacity to establish rover positions at intervals of as short as 0.2 s. On the other hand, establishing reference points in a static survey requires a substantially longer time. In most cases, the accuracy of a kinematic survey is dissimilar from that of a static survey [17]. In this study, the rapid static survey method was used to establish the reference point, and the coastline reference points were observed using the RTK method. As shown in Figure 2, the Ground Control Points (GCPs) were subjected to observation.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Preparation

In this study, the reference distance values were compared with Landsat 8 OLI images created within the context of GIS (coastline values from Landsat 8 OLI in correspondence to the coastline from GCPs). ArcGIS 10.1 was used for this study's

data conversion and preparation. The same horizontal data were used for both data sets in this study. The reference data of the research site were converted into the same projection system—zone 38 north of the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM). In particular, WGS1984 represented this study’s geodetic and spheroid.

Fig. 2. Coastline reference of GPS using the RTK method.

B. Pan-sharpening Algorithms

Numerous algorithms have been developed with the objective of creating a perfect spatial resolution MS image through the combination of PAN and MS bands. The process involved is known as pan-sharpening [18]. As a data fusion technique, pan-sharpening involves the high spatial resolution of a PAN image and the coarse spatial resolution of an MS image to construct a sharpened MS image with the same spatial resolution as the PAN image. Pan-sharpening enhances spatial resolution and retains the spectral characteristic of the primary MS image [19, 20]. The combination of Landsat ETM and MS and PAN bands typically involves this process of pan-sharpening for improved land use or cover mapping, precision farming, environment monitoring, forest management inventory, and urban areas scoping [20-24]. Accordingly, there are 7 MS bands with a spatial resolution of 30 m and a PAN band with a spatial resolution of 15 m in the recently released Landsat 8 OLI images [25]. With that, the use of pan-sharpening on Landsat 8 30 m MS image and the 15 m PAN band generates a 15 m spatial resolution-fused MS image.

Fig. 3. The proposed pan-sharpening method for Study using GIS.

C. Water Indexes

1) Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)

NDWI [26] is frequently used to detect remotely sensed coastlines. This index highlights the presence of water in a remotely sensed image using the green band and NIR band [26, 27].

$$NDWI = \frac{\rho_{Green} - \rho_{NIR}}{\rho_{Green} + \rho_{NIR}} \tag{1}$$

where ρ_{Green} is the reflectance value of the green band in the MS image and ρ_{NIR} is the reflectance value of the NIR band in the MS image.

This index uses green wavelengths to enhance water reflectance, reduce NIR reflectance by water features, and maximize NIR reflectance by vegetation and soil features. Hence, water characteristics are accentuated, while vegetation and soil are repressed. The calculated index ranges between 0 and 1. A negative value indicates a non-water surface, while a positive value indicates a water surface. An MS image with one green band and one NIR band can be used to determine the NDWI [26].

2) Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI)

MNDWI deals with the limitations of NDWI that often fail to distinguish water-related information from built-up land noise, resulting in the overemphasis of the extracted water areas. Apart from enhancing open water features, the use of MNDWI can effectively suppress and eliminate built-up land noise, vegetation noise, and soil noise. The strengths of MNDWI in reducing and eliminating built-up land noise make it a preferred choice when it comes to the need to augment and extract water-related information for a water area with its background dominated by built-up land areas [28]. The index is expressed as:

$$MNDWI = \frac{\rho_{Green} - \rho_{MIR}}{\rho_{Green} + \rho_{MIR}} \tag{2}$$

where ρ_{Green} is the reflectance value of the green band in the MS image and ρ_{MIR} is the Middle-Infrared Band.

In comparison to NDWI, MNDWI yields a significantly wider contrast between water and built-up land due to the increase of water feature values and the decrease of built-up land values (from positive to negative). Greater enhancement of water in the MNDWI image results in higher accuracy in the extraction of open water features considering the negative values of built-up land, soil, and vegetation.

D. Statistical Analysis

The assessment of Landsat 8 OLI in this study involved a statistical approach. Statistical analysis can enhance the interpretation of Landsat 8 OLI and GPS dataset correlations, trends, and error propagation. The difference in values between the coastline of Landsat 8 OLI and the coastline reference of GPS would generate the distance error for each point:

$$D_{Diff} = D_{Model} - D_{Reference} \quad (3)$$

where D_{Diff} is the distance difference, D_{Model} is the coastline model of Landsat 8 OLI and $D_{Reference}$ is the coastline reference of GPS.

Mean Error (ME), Standard Deviation (STD), and RMSE, which are commonly used to evaluate the precision of continuous variables, were computed for each model.

$$ME = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{D_{diff}}{N} \quad (4)$$

$$STD = \sqrt{\frac{(D_{diff} - ME)^2}{N-1}} \quad (5)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(D_{diff})^2}{N}} \quad (6)$$

Accordingly, RMSE is associated with the assessment of surface quality and indicates the differences between variables (predicted by the model and observed data), where N denotes the total element number [29]. The reference distance values were compared with Landsat 8 data.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current study primarily focused on determining the distance error values in terms of STD and RMSE for each point between the coastline of Landsat 8 OLI and the reference coastline of GPS. MS Excel and GIS were used. This study gathered Landsat 8 OLI from the USGS website. All distances were measured using GIS. Methods to extract coastline from Landsat 8 OLI bands were developed. MS band (Red, Green, and Blue), NIR band, and Panchromatic (PAN) band of Landsat 8 OLI image were primarily used in this study. The green band and NIR band were used to calculate NDWI from (1). Through the combination of Landsat 8 OLI and MS and PAN bands, the use of pan-sharpening algorithm produced a 15 m sharpened MS image. Following that, the original Landsat 8 OLI-MS bands were utilized to calculate MNDWI images with (2). Finally, the conversion of water/non-water images into the vector format was performed using ArcGIS to extract the coastline (Figure 4). Table II summarizes the obtained statistical results.

TABLE II. STATISTICAL RESULTS OF THE VALIDATION OF DISTANCE VALUES FOR LANDSAT 8 OLI IMAGE

Index	Min.	Max.	Mean	STD	RMSE	Min.
MNDWI	0.62	3.153	2.156	2.466	2.363	0.62
NDWI	0.622	3.167	2.304	2.606	2.491	0.622

Fig. 4. Strategy used to calculate the coastline from the Landsat 8 OLI image.

In particular, the MNDWI index recorded higher accuracy (STD = 2.466, RMSE = 2.363) than the NDWI (STD = 2.606, RMSE = 2.491). The use of pan-sharpening algorithm in this study generated sharpened MS images in standard false color at a spatial resolution of 15 m. As previously shown in Figure 3, the original 30 m MS image and 15 m PAN image were subjected to statistical analysis. The MS RGB bands 2, 3, and 4 in the Landsat 8 OLI image were used for this purpose.

The generated fused MS images were then used for the generation of the corresponding NDWI and MDWI images, which are provided in Figure 6. Critical spectral distortion of bands 3 and 5 was observed for the case of pan-sharpening algorithms. As a result, this study found indistinguishable water and non-water features in the calculated NDWI images, as depicted in Figure 6(b) (within the red circles).

V. CONCLUSION

The novelty of this study is that it employs highly accurate GPS data to provide a precise evaluation of the coastline that has been previously extracted by researchers [11, 28]. Statistical analysis focused on the distance values for each index in terms of STD and RMSE between GPS and Landsat 8 OLI images. Minimum value, maximum value, and ME were considered. The distance between the coastline of Landsat 8 OLI and the reference coastline of GPS was first calculated. Statistically, MDWI (RMSE of 2.363 m) recorded higher accuracy than NDWI (RMSE = 2.491). Based on the obtained results, this study presented an accurate statistical evaluation of determining the error in coastline extraction through the use of Landsat 8 OLI images, which would benefit researchers and practitioners in data construction and analysis. Moreover, this study demonstrated the promising potential of using Landsat 8

OLI in coastline identification. The cost- and time-effectiveness of Landsat 8 OLI make it a crucial tool when it comes to inundation maps and other applications.

Fig. 5. Distance difference between the coastline reference of GPS and the coastline of Landsat 8 OLI by (a) MNDWI and (b) NDWI.

Fig. 6. Water and non-water feature maps by (a) MNDWI and (b) NDWI using GIS.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

H. Tahir and A. H. M. Din jointly planned and designed the study. H. Tahir analyzed the data and authored the first draft of

the manuscript, whereas A. H. M. Din provided essential data and facilities and significantly contributed to discussion, data analysis, and test preparation.

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The Effect of Seismic Load on TBM Structures for Metro Line 3 in Hanoi, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Metro line 3 in Hanoi is being constructed using tunnels, which may affect nearby constructions. In addition, Hanoi's earthquakes also pose risks to this Tunnel Boring Machine (TBM) line. This paper studies the impact of TBM construction on the surrounding houses along the line, as well as the impact of earthquakes on this line. A 3D numerical model was developed to simulate the static and dynamic behavior of TBM at station 9 in Metro Line 3. The results show that the maximum settlement at the ground surface under seismic load is significantly reduced from 4.6 mm to 0.1 mm when using the jet grouting method.

Keywords-3D Plaxis; seismic; FEM; soil dynamic; structures

I. INTRODUCTION

The urban railway line 3 is a part of the Hanoi Metro network and is currently under construction. It will be the second line to be utilized in the Metro network, aimed to serve in and around Hanoi. The line will run from Nhon station to Hanoi station on a dedicated track with a total length of about 12.5 km, 8.5 km elevated and 4 km underground, and includes 12 stations in total. The line has two transfer stations. The elevated section of Metro Line No. 3 from Nhon to the S8 station at the University of Transport and Communications is 8.5 km long. The remaining 4 km-long underground section is under construction (S9 to S12).

For the underground section, the Tunnel Boring Machine (TBM) will be used and begin boring from the S9 station on Kim Ma Street to the S12 station at the Hanoi Train Station, which is located at the end of Tran Hung Dao Street. The TBM passes through a densely populated residential area with buildings above it between stations 9 and 10. The raft foundation type is commonly used in the buildings above Station 9. For Station 10, the foundation type varies depending on the height of the building. For buildings with a height of 5-7 floors, the foundation depth is about 10 m to 15 m and the driven pile foundation was used. For 7-story buildings, the foundation depth is about 15 m to 20 m and bored pile foundation was applied (Figure 1).

The construction of the TBM line passing through buildings can cause soil displacement and damage to the buildings' structure or foundation. This issue needs to be analyzed and monitored during the TBM construction process to ensure the safety of nearby structures [1-3].

The full dynamic analysis of tunnel structures under seismic loads has been studied extensively. The current trend is to use numerical analysis techniques. Authors in [4] used PLAXIS 3D to simulate the construction procedure of a TBM tunnel passing between existing piled footings located at variable distances from the tunnel. They concluded that the minimum distance between the tunnel and the piled footing was 3 m for piles with a diameter of 0.9 m and 2.5 m for a diameter of 1.5 m to minimize the effect of TBM construction on nearby pile foundations. In some cases, ground subsidence occurred when using TBM excavation, for example, in January 2008, while tunneling ring N0.200 of Chengdu metro line 1, ground subsidence occurred in one section. The distance between the surface and the top of the EPB TBM cutterhead was approximately 12.5 m. The maximum diameter of the subsidence area was 3 - 5 m behind the cutterhead [5]. Authors in [6] suggested that the variability in small-strain shear modulus of clay can have a significant impact on the seismic responses of the bending moment, shear force, and lateral deformation of rectangular tunnel walls to varying degrees. Authors in [7] evaluated the seismic loading of nearby

structures according to the Czech technical standards. Authors in [8] suggested the economic earthquake resistance construction of high-rise buildings.

Fig. 1. TBM will pass through the houses above (from Station 9 to Station 10).

Fig. 2. TBM for station 9 to station 10 (modified from [12]).

Fig. 3. (a) Geological profile, (b) grain size distribution curve for soils.

Limited research has been conducted in Vietnam on tunnel structures subjected to seismic loads. The analysis of TBM

only considers settlement and horizontal displacement. For instance, the ground surface settlement profile associated with the twin tunnels was analyzed using Plaxis 2D software in [9]. The numerical back-analysis was carried out using contraction and stress reduction methods. Other studies concentrated on the assessment of soil liquefaction [10, 11].

Further in-depth studies are required to investigate the stability calculations as an appropriate acceleration spectrum has not yet been provided. Therefore, this paper will study the impact of the construction stage of TBM on nearby buildings and the effect of earthquakes on TBM structures.

II. GROUND CONDITION

The geological units encountered along the tunnel alignment were collected from technical documents. There is a total of 6 soil layers in the project area (Figure 3). The summarized general description for each layer follows:

- Backfill: Sandy clay, brick, sand. This layer distributes on the ground surface in all boreholes. The thickness of the backfill layer varies from 1.0 to 3.5 m, with an average thickness of 1.93 m.
- Fine-grained materials:
 - GU1: Lean clay with lenses of silt or clayey silt (CL, CH) located at a depth less than 25 m from the surface. The thickness varies from 2.0 to 12.3 m, with 5.3 m average thickness. SPT value in average is $N_{30} = 16$.
 - GU3&4: Organic fat and elastic clay (CH, MH, ML, CL). The thickness varies from 1.7 to 14.9 m and the average thickness is 7.74 m. The SPT value in average is $N_{30} = 4$.
- Coarse-grained materials:
 - GU5_a: Loose to medium dense fine sand or silty sand (SC, SC-SM, SP), $N_{spt} < 30$. The thickness varies from 7.7 to 15.7 m, the average thickness is 11.93 m. The SPT value in average is $N_{30} = 20$.
 - GU5_b: Dense fine sand or silty sand (SP, SC-SM, SW). The thickness varies from 1.0 to 7.7 m and the average thickness is 3.6 m. The SPT value in average is $N_{30} = 43$.
 - GU7&8: Very dense sand and gravel (GP, SM). The thickness varies from 7.4 to 8.9 m and the average thickness is 8.3 m. The SPT value in average is $N_{30} > 50$.

During the soil investigation, the groundwater level was monitored using standpipe piezometers and observation wells. Based on the groundwater monitoring results at standpipe piezometers, the groundwater table was found to range from 10 to 12 m below ground level. This paper focuses on the analysis of the TBM line from Station 9 to Station 10 as shown in Figure 3. The typical section of geological at Station 9 is shown in Figure 3(a). The grain size distribution curves of the soil layer are shown in Figure 3(b).

III. CONSTRUCTION METHOD

Based on the soil distribution curve (Figure 3(b)), it is recommended that an Earth Pressure Balance (EPB) TBM is used for the construction of the Nhon - Hanoi train station. It is the first of its kind to be used in Hanoi. The TBM is designed to tunnel through highly urbanized areas and avoid collapses on the above surface. It is over 100 m long and weighs about 850 tons [12]. The TBM includes earth pressure balance shields that minimize impact on geological features, and it is expected that local houses will not be affected during the boring process.

IV. DYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF TBM

A. Input Parameters for Soil Layers and TBM Model

An 80 m × 80 m × 40 m soil strata was considered for modeling (Figure 4).

The dimensions of the model considered the effect of the depth tunnel and diameter of TBM [13]. The model boundaries were considered as free at the top and completely hinged constraints at the bottom, right, and left of the model edges. Standard fixities and absorbent boundaries were applied to reduce wave reflection at the boundaries. To model the soil behavior, the Hardening Soil (HS) model was used for all soil layers. The properties of the different soil layers are given in Table I. The dynamic load is assigned as the modified acceleration of the Dien Bien earthquake [14].

TABLE I. SOIL PARAMETERS IN PLAXIS 3D

Layer	GU1_s,d	GU3,4	GU5_a	GU5_b	GU7,8
	Lean clay	Organic clay	Loose to medium dense fine sand	Dense fine sand	Very dense sand or gravel
Model	HS	HS	HS	HS	HS
Drained type	UD	UD	UD	D	D
γ (kN/m ³)	19	18	20	21	21
Effective cohesion c' (kPa)	15	10	0	0	0
Internal friction angle ϕ' (deg)	25	20	32	33	40
ν	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3
E_{s0}^{ref} (MPa)	10	7	10	15	45
E_{oed}^{ref} (MPa)	10	7	10	15	45
E_{ur}^{ref}	30	21	50	75	135
m	1	1	0.8	0.8	0.5
Cc	0.0345	0.05	0.0345	0.023	0.007
Cs	0.01	0.015	0.006	0.004	0.002

Note: c' , ϕ' from CU-Triaxial test, UD: Undrained, D: Drained

TABLE II. TBM INPUT PARAMETERS

Parameter	Unit	Value
Tunnel diameter (inner/outer)	m	5.7/6.3
Modulus of elasticity of tunnel concrete	kPa	3.5E+7
Poisson's ratio	-	0.2

The studied section considers tunnels of 6.3 m diameter and -23 m from the ground level. The input parameter of TBM for analysis in Plaxis 3D is shown in Table II. The model for the

lining tunnel is the linear elastic model. The material of the lining tunnel is the plate element in Plaxis 3D. In PLAXIS 3D, it is feasible to conduct a dynamic analysis after a series of plastic calculations. The dynamic load applied is the product of the input value of the defined dynamic load and the corresponding dynamic load multiplier. The basic equation for the time-dependent movement of a volume under the influence of a (dynamic) load is:

$$M \ddot{u} + C \dot{u} + Ku = F \tag{1}$$

where M is the mass matrix, u is the displacement vector, C is the damping matrix, K is the stiffness matrix, and F is the load vector. Displacement u , velocity \dot{u} , and acceleration \ddot{u} , can vary with time.

In this research, the modified accelerations for Hanoi city were used to analyze the TBM structure between S9 and S10 for underground sections.

Fig. 4. Details of the TBM model in Plaxis 3D.

B. Plaxis 3D Calculations

The calculation of the model was conducted in 3 cases:

- Case 1: Tunnel excavation without jet grouting.
- Case 2: Tunnel excavation using TBM, ground improvement by using jet grouting.
- Case 3: Earthquake.

The construction sequence taken into consideration in the numerical model is:

- Step 1: Condition initialization.
- Step 2: Tunnel lining construction simulation by activating the tunnel lining and deactivating the soil clusters inside the tunnel.
- Step 3: Contraction simulates the volume loss, which was taken as 0.5%.
- Step 4: Seismic loading is applied for TBM (the modified acceleration for Hanoi city was applied, using Dynamic multipliers in Plaxis).

V. RESULTS

The maximum value for the static case was obtained from the last stage, while for the dynamic case, it was

obtained from the response spectrum. The analysis results are summarized in Table III.

A. Static Analysis

The calculation results of the 3D model show that the vertical displacement u_z when using jet grouting decreases significantly compared to the case without soil improvement (Figures 5-6). This result is in accordance with [2, 15].

Fig. 5. Total displacement during TBM excavation in case 1.

Fig. 6. Total displacement during TBM excavation in case 2.

B. Dynamic Analysis

Fig. 7. Vertical displacement due to seismic loading for normal conditions without jet grouting (case 3).

The maximum settlement at the ground surface is significantly reduced from 4.6 to 0.1 mm under seismic load. Figure 7 presents the vertical displacement of the soil due to seismic loading. A small value of displacement was observed and it did not affect the settlement of the house. The maximum velocity of the two cases is still less than that requirement for civil engineering (20 mm) [16].

TABLE III. RESULTS FOR STATIC AND SEISMIC CONDITIONS OF TBM

Parameter	Under static conditions		Under seismic loading	
	Without jet grouting	With Jet grouting	Without jet grouting	With jet grouting
Vertical displacement, u_z (mm)	60	37.8	5.2	4.7
Maximum settlement at ground level (mm)	21	6.5	4.6	0.1
Velocity v_x at ground level (mm/s)	-	-	7	0.8
Moment M11 of TBM (kN.m/m)	118	104	-	-

VI. CONCLUSION

The current study employed a complete 3D FEM model of a single TBM to investigate the influence of effective EPB-TBM parameters during excavation. The TBM construction of Metro Line 3, Hanoi, Vietnam under both normal and earthquake conditions was considered.

The maximum vertical displacement is 60 mm and 37.8 mm for the cases without and with jet grouting, respectively. It is necessary to monitor this displacement value during the construction process.

According to the results of Plaxis 3D analysis, the maximum settlement at the ground surface was reduced significantly from 4.6 to 0.1 mm under seismic load. Although a small value of displacement was observed, it had no effect on the house settlement. The maximum velocity when considering earthquake was considered was less than 20 mm, therefore it does not affect the structure. Additional future analysis should be performed to compare monitoring results and numerical analysis results.

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RIOD: Reinforced Image-based Object Detection for Unruly Weather Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Deep Neural Network (DNN) object detectors have proved their efficiency in the detection and classification of objects in normal weather. However, these models suffer a lot during bad weather conditions (foggy, rain, haze, night, etc.). This study presents a new scheme to reduce the aforementioned issue by attenuating the noise in the input image before feeding it to any kind of neural network-based object detector. In this study, the image optimization function transforms subpar-quality images due to bad weather into pictures with the optimal possible quality by estimating the proper illumination and transmission function. These optimized images showed improved object detection rates in the YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 models. This improvement in object detection was also noticed in the case of video input. This scheme was tested with images/videos from various weather conditions, and the results showed an encouraging improvement in detection rates.

Keywords-self-driving vehicle; YOLOv4; YOLOv5; image pre-processing; deep learning; object detection

I. INTRODUCTION

Object recognition with bounding boxes mentioning its class has numerous implementations in robotics, self-driving vehicles, drones, advanced driver assistant systems, etc. Current algorithms are good at handling camera inputs and identifying multiclass objects in both image and video. Recent studies have shown that these detectors severely underperform in challenging weather conditions, such as snow, rain, fog, etc. This performance decrease is ascribable to the subpar quality image input from the cameras due to reduced illumination and increased noise. In the case of autonomous vehicles, input images or video sequences can have sizeable variations in quality due to the type of camera used, its position, as well as the environmental conditions. Contemporary object detectors based on neural networks are trained and tested in general with appropriately illuminated images. The performance of these object detectors suffers greatly in challenging weather conditions due to low-quality image input. Unfortunately, this is the real-time scenario in most automated applications. In self-driving applications, training a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based model with all possible environmental conditions and scenarios is nearly impossible. Figure 1 shows a

few samples of bad situations that can be encountered while driving.

Global research on addressing this issue has been streamlined into three major strategies, which are sensor fusion, image preprocessing, and domain adaptation. The conventional approach of depending only on the input from the camera has been shown to be inadequate in bad weather conditions. Sensor fusion is another strategy to improve object detection. In [1], the fusion of a camera, lidar, and radar was used to complement each other for object detection in the most possible scenarios of driving. The major setback of this strategy is the scarcely available datasets using this combination of sensors. Furthermore, incorporating multiple sensors into an automobile is not cost-effective and can spoil its aesthetics. The change in environmental conditions can be considered a domain shift. A few models that rely on domain adaptation have been proposed for object detection at critical points. Such models demand enormous training datasets, and the annotation of such data is an intricate process. In addition, the use of synthetic datasets has emerged to be a failure due to the decrease in performance when tested in real-time.

Image preprocessing is another way to enhance the attenuated camera images before they are fed into CNN models. In [1-3], it was shown that existing preprocessing strategies developed, trained, and tested using more or less synthetic datasets tend to be unreliable in real-world conditions, particularly for moving objects. In this study, the issue of object detection and classification in bad weather conditions was addressed by incorporating an image preprocessing unit into the object detectors, called Reinforced Image Object Detector (RIOD). The image preprocessing unit works by eliminating noise from the camera output and producing a clearer image, which is then fed to the object detector. As predicting the input domain or situation of the scene is almost impossible, it would be appropriate to remove the noise from the attenuated images and, therefore, improve the performance of the object detectors. The scope of this study can be summarized as follows:

- Designing an image reinforcement filter and using it before the object detectors. Based on certain variables, this filter can transform subpar images from the camera into images with proper illumination and better quality.
- Training the "You Only Look Once" (YOLO) v4 and v5 models with annotated datasets consisting of images under varying conditions i.e., fog, night, day, rain, haze, etc.
- Testing by filtering and reinforcing the data from the sensor. This reinforced image/video is then fed to the YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 models for object detection and classification.
- Perform several iterations, separately for images and video inputs, with YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 models to investigate the results of the proposed method in object detection and classification with the camera as the sole input sensor.

Fig. 1. Images representing the harsh driving scenarios under bad weather conditions. These images are samples collected from the DAWN dataset [4].

II. RELATED WORKS

Object detectors that rely on the deep CNN concept have produced excellent results in detecting objects with bounding boxes and labels. However, these models cannot be employed directly in certain applications, such as autonomous vehicles. In

this case, image quality and visibility are highly dependent on environmental conditions. Object detectors can be broadly classified into two groups: single-stage and two-stage detectors. Single-stage detectors are faster in operation than two-stage detectors. Single-Shot multi-box Detector (SSD) [5] and YOLO [6] are two common single-stage object detectors.

Many researchers work on domain adaptation to improve object detection and classification in harsh climate conditions. In [7], the existing faster Region-based CNN (R-CNN) model was complemented with domain adaptive components (image and instance level shift), showing a slight performance improvement under all climate conditions. Although there is a slight performance improvement, R-CNN is slow in processing compared to the YOLO detectors [8]. In [9], domain-adaptive components were integrated into the YOLOv4 backbone at three different levels. This model exhibited a certain level of improvement in detecting objects compared to the original YOLOv4. In [10], a plug-and-play module, called cross-fusion, was added to the YOLOv5 model to combine the features of multiple convolutional layers, but its improved performance came at the cost of increased computational complexity. In [11-12], a multimodal sensor fusion technique was proposed, which presented an enhanced object detection rate for autonomous vehicles. However, the integration of four different sensors and the simultaneous processing of their outputs in real time proves to be cumbersome and expensive compared to other methods.

III. REINFORCED IMAGE OBJECT DETECTOR

YOLO is one of the fastest object-detecting models and has multiple versions. This study used YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 as baseline models, as they exhibit enhanced object detection performance when provided with good-quality images as input [13]. YOLOv4 [14], is a fast-operating object detection system that can be compared to a human body, with CSPDarknet53 being the backbone of the system that extracts multiple features. These features are collected by the layers called Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) and Path Aggregation Network (PAN), which are the neck of the arrangement. This is further fed to the head of the system which is the original YOLOv3. After surveying these features, the head annotates the bounding boxes as well as the probabilities of the class of each box.

YOLOv5 is a faster and more lightweight object detection system that is more suitable for real-time applications. This system relies on a similar three-layer architecture comprising the backbone, neck, and head. The YOLOv5 architecture uses a focus structure with CSPDarknet53 as its backbone, which increases its speed and adds features like data augmentation and auto-learning bounding boxes. The weight files of YOLOv5 are significantly smaller than those of YOLOv4, making YOLOv5 faster and easier to handle. In the proposed RIOD-YOLO, the image/video is preprocessed with the help of image enhancement filter banks before feeding to the object detectors, to ensure that the performance of these detectors is kept stable irrespective of the driving scenario, namely fog, rain, night, day, etc.

A. Filter Design for Image-Enhancement

The output of the sensor, namely the camera output, is directed to the image preprocessing filter. This filter cleans up

the noisy image that is captured under undesirable weather conditions. These refined images are further tested for object detection using the YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 models. In this study, YOLOv4 was trained and tested with a custom dataset, collected specifically for autonomous vehicle applications, and YOLOv5 was tested with trained weights. During bad weather conditions, the images captured by the camera suffer a lot due to low visibility. These subpar images can be upgraded with the help of boundary conditions and regularizations [15]. The filter, designed as in [15], can perform scene transmission, regularization, and optimization to reduce noise and increase overall quality of the image. This filter can be used as a separate module and work as a ready-to-use image enhancer for any CNN model. The brightness of any pixel captured by the camera under any climatic condition can be derived as [15-17]:

$$R(x) = L(x)T(x) + A[1 - T(x)] \quad (1)$$

where $R(x)$ represents the captured pixel value, $L(x)$ is the luminosity of the scene, $T(x)$ is the scene transmission that describes the light that has reached the camera without getting scattered, and A is the atmospheric light. The objective is to recover $L(x)$ from (1), which requires an estimation of the transmission function $T(x)$ and the atmospheric light A . From (1), the scene can be recovered as:

$$L(x) = \frac{R(x)-A}{T(x)} + A \quad (2)$$

Thus, every x , $L(x)$ can be determined from (2) using the transmission function $T(x)$, quantified based on the boundary constraints specified in [15], and by estimating the atmospheric light A . Let us consider that $L(x)$ is bounded between two vectors C_0 and C_1 that have valid radiance values for every image. This in turn leaves a boundary constraint on $T(x)$. Using the concept of extrapolation, a boundary constraint $Lb(x)$ is worked out for every pixel x , and the lower bound $Tb(x)$ is determined by rearranging (2) as:

$$\frac{1}{T(x)} = \frac{\|L(x)-A\|}{\|R(x)-A\|} \quad (3)$$

The lower bound $Tb(x)$ ensures that the extrapolated values lie within the radiance vector values, therefore:

$$Tb(x) \leq T(x) \leq 1 \quad (4)$$

This implies that the extrapolated values for each pixel x must be within $[Tb(x), 1]$. $Tb(x)$ is further worked out as [15]:

$$T_b(x) = \min\{\max_{c \in \{r,g,b\}} \left(\frac{A_c - R_c(x)}{A_c - C_{c0}}, \frac{A_c - R_c(x)}{A_c - C_{c1}} \right), 1\} \quad (5)$$

This includes determining the smallest of the two terms, which are based on the color channels (RGB) and factors such as atmospheric light A , pixel intensity $R(x)$, and radiance bound C_{c0} and C_{c1} . Scene transmission $T(x)$ is substantially regularized to enhance the quality of dehazing. This approach employs weighted constraints between adjacent pixels:

$$W(x, y)[T(x) - T(y)] \quad (6)$$

where x and y are two adjacent pixels. The $w(x, y)$ controls the influence of constraints and ensures that similar neighboring pixels have similar transmission values. A bank of higher-order differential filters is used to calculate the weighting function in discrete form. The atmospheric light is estimated by applying a minimum filter to each color channel of the input image and then selecting the maximum value from each channel.

B. RIOD Architecture

Rather than complicating the design of Deep Neural Networks (DNN) [9-12, 18-19], a separate filter was developed to be placed between the camera and the CNN module. This filter mechanism enriches the image captured by the camera and feeds it to CNN models, as shown in Figure 2. This filter arrangement works efficiently for both image and video input. As mentioned above, this filtering mechanism reinforces the input image to the CNN model and, in turn, increases the object detection rate, particularly in adverse climate conditions.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

The YOLOv4 and YOLOv5 models were trained and tested with a custom dataset, consisting of 5232 images collected from a variety of datasets including Dawn, Udacity [20], BDD100k [21], and the Indian driving dataset [22]. The dataset includes images under various climate conditions, such as rain, fog, haze, night, and day. The models were tested using the custom dataset to detect 9 classes of objects, namely car, van, truck, traffic light, person, motorcycle, bus, and bicycle. The tests were carried out on standalone YOLO and RIOD-YOLO.

Fig. 2. RIOD architecture: A filter is placed between the camera and the CNN models, enhancing the image before feeding into the YOLO-based object detector. The output from the YOLO-based detector shows the multi-box classification of objects. The chosen images are from the DAWN dataset [4].

Fig. 3. Reinforced filter output for different climatic conditions such as fog, rain, and snow. All images are from the DAWN dataset [4].

Fig. 4. Object detection under various climatic conditions: (a) input image, (b) object detection using customized YOLOv4, (c) RIOD using YOLOv4, and (d) RIOD using YOLOv5. All images are from the DAWN dataset [4].

A. Setup 1

The original YOLOv4 model with CSPdarknet53 as its backbone was initialized with a pre-trained weight file. The weights were updated by training the model using a custom dataset in batches of 64 images with a learning rate of 0.0001. This updated custom weight file was then used to test the model. Table I shows the test results. The reinforcement filter

was mapped out based on the notion of extrapolation. First, the input images were passed through the reinforcement filter before being sent to the YOLO models for testing. Figure 3 compares the input and the corresponding output of the reinforcement filter for every image. These reinforced images are then fed into the customized YOLOv4 model for testing. Figure 4 shows the improvement in object detection rate after using the reinforcement filter in various climatic conditions.

B. Setup 2

The reinforcement filter functions as a plug-and-play module that can work with different versions of YOLO. In this iteration, the filter was attached to the YOLOv5 model, which was tested with both a pre-trained weight file (YOLOv5s) and a customized weight file. Figure 4 shows the improvement in object detection rate after attaching the reinforcement filter.

C. Evaluation Parameters

The performance was measured and quantitatively evaluated using average Precision (P) and Mean Average Precision (MAP). Their computation procedure was:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (7)$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (8)$$

where TP represents true positive, FP also false positive, and FN also false negative. The Average Precision (AP) is given by:

$$AP = \int_0^1 P(R) dR \quad (9)$$

The Mean Average Precision (MAP) is given by:

$$MAP = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{x \in N} AP_x \quad (10)$$

where N is the number of object classes. The models were tested with the custom dataset, consisting of randomly selected images under a variety of climatic conditions, and Table I shows the MAP values.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT CNN METHODS

Method	Dataset	Classes						MAP
		C	B	V	TL	P	MC	
Domain adaptive faster R-CNN [7]	Cityscapes	41	35	22	-	25	20	29
YOLOv4[6]	Cityscapes	47	30	-	-	32	17	31
(MS-DAYOLOV4) [9]	Cityscapes	56	36	-	-	39	29	40
Robost YOLOv3	Cityscapes	58	51	-	-	36	26	43
Robost YOLOvX	Cityscapes	61	57	-	-	45	42	51
YOLOv4	BDD100K	73	-	-	47	42	-	54
YOLOv4	INIT	74	-	-	48	45	-	56
RIOD-YOLOv4	custom dataset	65	41	22	16	26	70	40
RIOD-YOLOv5	custom dataset	78	77	60	43	60	75	65

column classes C: car, B: bus, V: van, TL: traffic light, P: person, MC: motorcycle

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed RIOD-YOLO aimed to improve object detection efficiency, particularly under adverse climatic conditions. In this method, the output from the sensor is fed to the image enhancement filter, which comprehensively improves the image quality before being fed to the object detectors, improving the rate of object detection. A customized dataset was used to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method, and the results clearly showed an improvement in the rate of object detection, especially under unfavorable climatic conditions. When compared to the baseline YOLO models, the proposed RIOD-YOLO produced promising results in every

aspect. The scope of RIOD-YOLO is not limited to just autonomous driving, as it can also be used in surveillance systems that use image/video input to improve visibility, especially in adverse weather conditions.

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Selection Criteria for Evaluating Predictive Maintenance Techniques for Rotating Machinery using the Analytic Hierarchical Process (AHP)

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ABSTRACT

A primary industry objective is to ensure that machinery remains operational through effective management. Predictive maintenance plays a significant role in monitoring the working condition of machinery. The goal of this study is to establish the criteria for evaluating predictive maintenance techniques for rotating machines utilizing the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). To achieve this target, survey data were collected from questionnaires and interviews with 20 experts, which had at least 20 years of professional experience. The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was utilized for criteria selection. The findings disclosed that predictive maintenance factors for rotating machines were ranked as follows: vibration analysis (45.5%), acoustic analysis (22.7%), oil analysis (22.4%), infrared thermography (5.8%), and wear particle analysis (3.6%). The Consistency Ratio (CR) was determined to be less than 10%, indicating a high level of consensus among the experts. Given the elevated importance attributed to vibration analysis, it can be concluded that the latter is the primary criterion for selecting predictive maintenance techniques for rotating machines.

Keywords-Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP); criteria; maintenance technique; rotating machinery

I. INTRODUCTION

Machinery is a significant part of the practical manufacturing process, both in quality and quantity. As machinery maintenance is necessary, selecting suitable maintenance techniques is a critical process that cannot be overlooked. Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) is an analytical process that assists in making complex decisions by splitting the problem into parts, creating a hierarchy structure. AHP uses information derived from key informants to define criteria, sort the factors by their rating and get the most critical

factor for the conclusion. A literature review on maintenance and criteria sorting showed that AHP is the most common approach [1] in machinery condition assessment and intermediate- and long-term maintenance to keep the machine at its highest efficiency [2].

Maintenance is a necessary process that has to be well managed. The first stage of maintenance management in manufacturing facilities is to select the most suitable maintenance strategy for effective machinery maintenance. This stage is unignorable [3]. Maintenance of machinery comes

in many forms, such as corrective maintenance, preventive maintenance, predictive maintenance, and proactive maintenance, depending on organizational strategies. Predictive maintenance is most investigated. It is the analysis of deterioration or the intensity of the existing decline. Well-analyzing predictive maintenance indicates whether further maintenance is needed [4, 5]. Predictive maintenance is also defined as a set of activities detecting the changes in the physical condition of equipment to properly conduct the maintenance task and thus maximize the equipment lifespan while reducing the failure risk [6]. The predictive maintenance program helps minimize the unscheduled breakdowns of all mechanical equipment in the plant and ensures that repaired equipment is in acceptable mechanical condition. Moreover, it facilitates the analysis of machine-train issues before they become serious. Predictive maintenance primarily concerns predicting the damages to the system by detecting early damage signs to enable maintenance tasks to be more proactive. It is acknowledged that most mechanical issues can be minimized if they are detected and repaired early. Besides acting before failure, predictive maintenance also intends to manage fault, although the system has no immediate damage, in order to ensure smooth operation and reduce energy consumption [7].

The introduction of advanced manufacturing technologies to increase automation and decline buffering time of inventory has increased the pressure on maintenance management. Maintenance experts require Maintenance Performance Indicators (MPI) to proceed with production activities effectively. For this reason, techniques based on the risk of equipment failure, maintenance cost, AHP, and Goal Programming (GP) have been introduced for MPI strategy selection [8]. AHP has been used for maintenance strategy selection in factories [3, 9] and has been applied along with other methods to solve such problems. The AHP is an effective tool for the decision-making process of sophisticated problems. It helps to structure complex issues hierarchically, causing the decision-making procedure to be simplified and speed up [10, 11]. It solves the problems by classifying them into variables, arranged in a hierarchical order. It assigns numerical values to subjective considerations about the significance of each element. It synthesizes the various considerations to evaluate which element has the highest priority (greatest importance) and impacts the circumstance. There are four steps of solving problems using AHP [12]. AHP has been utilized in decision-making processes of knowledge management implementation [8, 13], selecting data science methodology [14], and maintenance strategy [9]. Authors in [8] proposed the predictive maintenance effectiveness indicator based on AHP to identify the more compelling aspect of the maintenance approach. Authors in [6] investigated the Maintenance Policy Selection (MPS) using AHP. The study tested the practicality of the AHP-based MPS technique by conducting three workshops at three firms. The results demonstrated that AHP was well suited for MPS in this broad setting and provided a structured and detailed technique for MPS. Moreover, AHP facilitated the discussions during and after the sessions, offering a better understanding of the policy selection process. Moreover, authors in [5], applied AHP to obtain a criterion for

selecting the applicable spots for building weigh stations. The results demonstrated that engineering factors had the highest importance score among engineering, economic, and environment-social factors (60%). Meanwhile, the economic and environment-social factors had 25% and 15% importance scores, respectively. Considering engineering factors, the truck traffic volume had the highest importance score of 24%. The importance scores of proper constructive area, transport route, and international roughness index were 14%, 13%, and 9%, respectively. Of all the economic factors, lowering highway maintenance showcased the highest importance score of 10%. Regarding the environment-social factors, the highest importance score was that of the effect on community (8%), followed by the area suitability (4%) and pollution reduction (3%).

The literature review showed that AHP has been widely studied and applied as an accurate approach in determining the rating of the criteria and analyzing complex decision-making processes. However, there is no evidence of AHP being employed to establish criteria for selecting assessment techniques concerning predictive maintenance in rotating machines. This study explicitly targets five such primary criteria: vibration analysis, sound emissions analysis, oil analysis, infrared thermography, and wear particle analysis. AHP will be employed to determine the most crucial factors. The identified evaluation criteria will then guide the selection of predictive maintenance techniques.

II. PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE

Predictive maintenance uses techniques such as vibration analysis, acoustic emission/acoustic analysis, oil analysis, infrared thermography, and wear particle analysis to assess the equipment status. Technique selection depends on equipment, types, impact on the production, and on any other critical for the factor's operations aspects to achieve the predictive maintenance target [15]. The techniques employed by predictive maintenance are described below:

- Oil analysis: analysis of lubricating oil and formation of small particles to learn the status of bearings and gears.
- Vibration analysis: the most effective method for detecting rotating machine defects.
- Acoustic analysis: continuous detection, searching, and checking for cracks in the structure and piping.
- Infrared thermography: used to analyze the working machine and electrical equipment, as it can detect thermal or mechanical defects.
- Wear particle analysis: analyzing worn-out parts, such as pistons, gearboxes, or hydraulic systems. Wear particles that are chipped out will give information about the wear and tear of these parts.

III. METHODOLOGY

The process to get the suitable criteria for predictive maintenance technique assessment can be performed by studying information from related research and experts' feedback to get the connected central and sub-criteria. Then,

the questionnaire is constructed for the experts to analyze the importance of each factor before using the AHP. The result is a rating of each criterion that has been collected and screened and can be used for predictive maintenance technique assessment. The analysis result will yield sorted and suitable criteria as shown in Figure. 1.

Fig. 1. Assessment procedure for predictive maintenance.

Multiple Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) comprises various methodologies, such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Analytic Network Process (ANP), and TOPSIS (Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution), among others. However, AHP stands out due to its superior advantages over other methods. AHP is a decision-

making procedure grounded in analysis, involving the subdivision of problems into components and their hierarchical organization based on importance and impact. Essentially, AHP represents a specific method within a broader category in contrast to other MCDM methods. AHP distinctive features include its utilization of a hierarchical structure and pairwise comparisons to establish priorities. These characteristics contribute to AHP's effectiveness in decision-making processes, setting it apart from other methods within the MCDM framework. The AHP process steps are detailed below.

A. *Sorting Problems in Hierarchical Structure*

Complex problems can be examined thoroughly and in a structured way [16, 17]. In our case, the top level aims to select predictive maintenance techniques. At the bottom level, the decision alternatives can be found [14, 18], as shown in Figure. 2.

B. *Making a Questionnaire for Factor Importance Analysis*

Factors in criteria assessment for predictive maintenance of the rotating machines can be divided into criteria and sub-criteria. A questionnaire was given to experts to analyze the importance of each criterion [5, 19]. The questionnaire was developed based on requirements and suitability [4]. Twenty experts contributed to this research: 2 managing engineers, 10 maintenance engineers, and 8 repair technicians, each of them with at least 20 years of experience.

C. *Prioritization of Problems in Each Component*

This part assigns ratings to the components based on objective achievement. The higher rating component will receive higher priority. The first step is the collection of pairwise comparisons in a matrix form. After that, the problem is decomposed, there will be a comparison between the components, i.e. a comparison between the criteria and each criterion will be assigned a rating by cross-comparison [9, 14, 18]. Table I shows the established criteria and their comparison results. Tables II-VI illustrate the pair comparison findings for the sub criteria of each criterion, i.e. oil analysis, vibration analysis, sound emissions analysis, IR thermography, and wear particle analysis.

Fig. 2. Predictive maintenance criteria category division.

TABLE I. CRITERIA CALCULATION

Criteria	Oil analysis	Vibration analysis	Sound emission analysis	Infrared thermography	Wear particle analysis
Oil analysis	1	1/4	1/3	5	5
Vibration analysis	4	1	1	8	8
Sound emission analysis	3	1	1	8	8
Infrared thermography	1/5	1/8	1/8	1	2
Wear particle analysis	1/5	1/8	1/8	1/2	

TABLE II. PAIR COMPARISON MATRIX FOR OIL ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Viscosity	Density	Dielectric constant	Temperature
Viscosity	1	2	3	3
Density	1/2	1	2	1/2
Dielectric constant	1/3	1/2	1	1/3
Temperature	1/3	2	3	1

TABLE III. PAIR COMPARISON MATRIX FOR VIBRATION ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Frequency	Displacement, Velocity, Acceleration	Phase angle
Frequency	1	1	2
Displacement, Velocity, Acceleration	1	1	2
Phase angle	1/2	1/2	1

TABLE IV. PAIR COMPARISON MATRIX FOR ACOUSTIC ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Frequency	Power	Duration
Frequency	1	1	2
Power	1	1	2
Duration	1/2	1/2	1

TABLE V. PAIR COMPARISON MATRIX FOR INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

Sub-Criteria	Temperature measurement range	Temperature measuring distance	Camera precision
Temperature measurement range	1	1/2	1
Temperature measuring distance	2	1	1
Camera precision	1	1	

TABLE VI. PAIR COMPARISON MATRIX FOR WEAR PARTICLE ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Particle size	Wear surface	Wear surface color
Particle size	1	1/2	3
Wear surface	2	1	3
Wear surface color	1/3	1/3	1

D. Geometric Mean Method

The geometric mean calculation is carried out by multiplying the numbers and then taking the root of the result based on several numbers used.

$$V_i = \left(\prod_{j=1}^n a_{ij} \right) \tag{1}$$

where a_{ij} is the value of members in the matrix, V_i is the geometric mean, and n is the number of members used to calculate the average.

E. Rating Synthesis

This step synthesizes the total rating from the sub-criteria of each criterion after weighing. Generally, the rating analysis is conducted by:

$$W_i = \frac{V_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n V_i} \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n W_i = 1.0 \tag{3}$$

where W_i is the rating of each criterion, V_i is the geometric mean, and n is the number of members utilized to calculate the average.

F. Consistency Ratio

Consistency ratio calculation checks the reasoning consistency of the comparison results. The examination is completed by finding the consistency index. The processing steps are:

1. Calculate by multiplying the sum of the ratings of each criterion in the row with the total mean in the column, and then sum them all together. The result will be the number of all the criteria used for comparison:

$$\lambda_{\max} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} W_j \right] \tag{4}$$

If the consistency is 100%, then the number of criteria used for comparison is $\lambda_{\max} < (n)$. If the matrix table is not consistent, then $\lambda_{\max} > (n)$.

2. The consistency Index is calculated by:

$$CI = \frac{(\lambda_{\max} - n)}{(n - 1)} \tag{5}$$

3. The Random consistency Index (RI) is calculated. The result is shown in Table VII.

4. The Consistency Ratio (CR) is calculated from the ratio between the CI and RI:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \tag{6}$$

If the CR value is less than or equal to 0.10, it will be accepted.

TABLE VII. RANDOM CONSISTENCY INDEX (RI)

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
RI	0.00	0.00	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49

IV. A MANUAL AHP CALCULATION EXAMPLE

The presentation is provided in table form for simplicity reasons [12, 20]. This study employs five primary criteria, as depicted in Table VIII, illustrating the prioritization of predictive maintenance techniques by multiplying the rating of each main criterion with its corresponding sub-criteria. The

presented table indicates a negligible distinction between the results obtained through manual calculations and table-based calculations of AHP, affirming their suitability for prioritization [8, 21], as illustrated in Table IX. Subsequently, the matrices for each pair are compared and computed, as depicted in Table IX. Cross-assessment between the criteria is demonstrated in Tables IX-XVIII.

TABLE VIII. PAIRED COMPARISON MATRIX FOR PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE TECHNIQUE

Criteria	Oil analysis	Vibration analysis	Sound emission analysis	Infrared thermography	Wear particle analysis	Priority vector
Oil analysis	1.000	0.250	0.333	5.000	5.000	0.156
Vibration analysis	4.000	1.000	1.000	8.000	8.000	0.391
Sound emission analysis	3.000	1.000	1.000	8.000	8.000	0.367
Infrared thermography	0.200	0.125	0.125	1.000	2.000	0.049
Wear particle analysis	0.200	0.125	0.125	0.500	1.000	0.037

The matrix representing Table VIII is changed to a decimal number form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1.000 & 0.250 & 0.333 & 5.000 & 5.000 \\ 4.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 3.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 1.000 & 2.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 0.500 & 1.000 \end{bmatrix}$$

Iteration 1: Squaring the Matrix by (7):

$$A_j = \begin{bmatrix} a_{1j} & \dots & a_{1n_j} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{nj} & \dots & a_{nn_j} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W_i/W_j & \dots & W_n/W_n \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ \dots & \dots & \dots \\ W_n/W_n & \dots & W_n/W_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1.000 & 0.250 & 0.333 & 5.000 & 5.000 \\ 4.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 3.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 1.000 & 2.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 0.500 & 1.000 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\frac{W_i}{W_j} = a_{ij} \Rightarrow W_i = a_{ij}W_j, (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$, W_i is the input value in row i , and W_j is the input value in column j .

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 1.000 & 0.250 & 0.333 & 5.000 & 5.000 \\ 4.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 3.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 1.000 & 2.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 0.500 & 1.000 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\times \begin{bmatrix} 1.000 & 0.250 & 0.333 & 5.000 & 5.000 \\ 4.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 3.000 & 1.000 & 1.000 & 8.000 & 8.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 1.000 & 2.000 \\ 0.200 & 0.125 & 0.125 & 0.500 & 1.000 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, we get:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 4.999 & 2.083 & 2.166 & 17.164 & 24.668 \\ 14.200 & 5.000 & 5.332 & 48.000 & 60.000 \\ 13.200 & 4.750 & 4.999 & 43.000 & 55.000 \\ 1.675 & 0.675 & 0.693 & 5.000 & 7.000 \\ 1.375 & 0.488 & 0.504 & 4.000 & 5.000 \end{bmatrix}$$

The summaries of the geometric mean of consistency and of the criteria are given in Table IX and Table X, respectively.

TABLE IX. GEOMETRIC MEAN OF CONSISTENCY SUMMARY

Predictive technique	CR	Geometric Mean
Predictive technique	< 0.1	0.058
Oil analysis	< 0.1	0.029
Vibration analysis	< 0.1	0.012
Sound emission analysis	< 0.1	0.009
Infrared thermography	< 0.1	0.017
Wear particle analysis	< 0.1	0.026

TABLE X. GEOMETRIC MEAN OF THE CRITERIA SUMMARY

Main criteria	Global priority		
	Sub criteria	Priority (%)	Rank
Predictive maintenance technique	Vibration analysis	45.50%	1
	Sound emission analysis	22.70%	2
	Oil analysis	22.40%	3
	Infrared thermography	5.80%	4
	Wear particle analysis	3.60%	5

The Normal Value of the matrix is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 4.999 & 2.083 & 2.166 & 17.164 & 24.668 \\ 14.200 & 5.000 & 5.332 & 48.000 & 60.000 \\ 13.200 & 4.750 & 4.999 & 43.000 & 55.000 \\ 1.675 & 0.675 & 0.693 & 5.000 & 7.000 \\ 1.375 & 0.488 & 0.504 & 4.000 & 5.000 \end{bmatrix}$$

The sum of the rows is given in Table XI:

TABLE XI. ROW SUMS

	Row sum	Priority vector
	51.074	0.154
	132.532	0.400
	120.949	0.365
	15.043	0.045
	11.367	0.034
Totals	330.965	1.000

The difference of Table VIII and Iteration I can be seen in Table XII while the deduced criteria ranking is portrayed in Table XIII. The pair comparison matrices are exhibited in Tables XIV-XVIII and the summary in Table XIX.

TABLE XII. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN TABLE VIII AND ITERATION I

Table VIII	Iteration I	Difference
0.156	0.154	0.002
0.391	0.400	0.009
0.367	0.365	0.002
0.049	0.045	0.004
0.037	0.034	0.003

TABLE XIII. CRITERIA RANKING

Criteria	Table VIII	Iteration I	Rank
Oil analysis	0.156	0.156	3
Vibration analysis	0.391	0.391	1
Sound emission analysis	0.367	0.367	2
Infrared thermography	0.049	0.049	4
Wear particle analysis	0.037	0.037	5

TABLE XIV. PAIR COMPARISON FOR OIL ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Viscosity	Density	Dielectric constant	Temperature	Relative priority	Relative priority (%)
Viscosity	1.000	2.000	3.000	3.000	0.445	44.5%
Density	0.500	1.000	2.000	0.500	0.185	18.5%
Dielectric constant	0.333	0.500	1.000	0.333	0.106	10.6%
Temperature	0.333	2.000	3.000	1.000	0.445	4.45%

TABLE XV. PAIR COMPARISON FOR VIBRATION ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Frequency	Displacement, velocity, acceleration	Phase angle	Relative priority	Relative priority (%)
Frequency	1.000	1.000	2.000	0.400	40%
Displacement, velocity, acceleration	1.000	1.000	2.000	0.400	40%
Phase angle	0.500	0.500	1.000	0.200	20%

TABLE XVI. PAIR COMPARISON FOR SOUND EMISSION ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Frequency	Decibel	Duration time	Relative priority	Relative priority (%)
Frequency	1.000	1.000	2.000	0.400	40%
Power	1.000	1.000	2.000	0.400	40%
Duration time	0.500	0.500	1.000	0.200	20%

TABLE XVII. PAIR COMPARISON FOR INFRARED THERMOGRAPHY

Sub-Criteria	Temperature measurement range	Temperature measuring distance	Camera precision	Relative priority	Relative priority (%)
Temperature measurement range	1.000	0.500	1.000	0.261	26.1%
Temperature measuring distance	2.000	1.000	1.000	0.411	41.1%
Camera precision	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.328	32.8%

TABLE XVIII. PAIR COMPARISON FOR WEAR PARTICLE ANALYSIS

Sub-Criteria	Particle size	Wear surface	Wear surface color	Relative priority	Relative priority (%)
Particle size	1.000	0.500	3.000	0.334	33.4%
Wear surface	2.000	1.000	3.000	0.525	52.5%
Wear surface color	0.333	0.333	1.000	0.141	14.1%

TABLE XIX. GEOMETRIC MEAN OF SUB-CRITERIA SUMMARY

Global Priority							
Sub criteria	Distribution	Priority (%)	Rank	Sub criteria	Distribution	Priority (%)	Rank
Vibration analysis	Displacement, velocity, acceleration	49.80%	1	Oil analysis	Viscosity	40.80%	1
					Temperature	29.40%	2
	Frequency	40.50%	2		Density	21.50%	3
Phase angle	9.30%	3	Dielectric constant		8.20%	4	
Sound emission analysis	Power	45.50%	1	Infrared thermography	Temperature measuring distance	45.20%	1
					Camera precision	31.00%	2
	Frequency	40.50%	2	Wear particle analysis	Temperature measurement range	23.80%	3
					Wear surface	42.40%	1
					Particle size	33.90%	2
Duration time	14.00%	3	Wear surface color	23.80%	3		

The prioritization analysis of each criterion, coupled with consistency checks conducted by the 20 experts, indicated that the ratio remained consistent, with a Consistency Ratio (CR) not exceeding 10% (CR < 0.1) [16, 17, 22]. This underscores the robust consistency in the experts' reasoning.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to specify criteria for selecting predictive maintenance technique assessment for rotating machines based on the AHP. The study analyzed data obtained from questionnaires answered by experts in the field. The results

demonstrated that the factors in predictive maintenance techniques for rotating machines, sorted by rating in descending order, were vibration analysis (45.5%, the highest-rated), acoustic analysis (22.7%), oil analysis (22.4%), infrared thermography (5.8%) and wear particle analysis (3.6%). Consequently, vibration analysis is established as the main criterion for the selection and evaluation of predictive maintenance techniques for rotating machinery. An in-depth expert evaluation of the questionnaire focused on vibration analysis revealed that displacement, velocity and acceleration received the highest ratings at 49.8%, followed by frequency at 40.5% and phase angle at 9.3. Regarding sound analysis, the sub-criteria power received the highest rating at 45.5%, followed by frequency at 40.5% and duration time at 14%. In the domain of oil analysis, viscosity emerged as the top-rated sub-criterion at 40.8%, followed by temperature at 29.4%, density at 21.5%, and dielectric constant at 8.2%. Concerning the infrared thermography, the sub-criteria of temperature and distance measuring obtained the highest rating at 45.2%, followed by camera precision at 31% and temperature measurement range at 23.8%. In the sector of wear particle analysis, wear surface was rated the highest at 42.4%, followed by particle size at 33.9% and wear surface color at 23.8%. The consistency ratio, as indicated, remained below 10% (CR < 0.1), emphasizing a high level of consistency in the assessments.

VI. CONCLUSION

AHP-based assessment of predictive maintenance criteria was tested in two factories. The process started with data collection through interviews and surveys. Then, the data were used for model development and identification of the most essential criteria for problem assessment. The hierarchy was developed with participation from the decision-makers, and then the comparison consistent with the requirements and prioritization was performed. This study focused on using multiple-criteria decisions in maintenance, particularly that of rotating machines. To further the study, we suggest utilizing this model for all maintenance types as an efficient tool in the decision-making process.

AHP usage in defining criteria for selecting assessment techniques in predictive maintenance for rotating machinery has gained considerable attention from the research community. The current study's emphasis is clearly delineated across five fundamental criteria: vibration analysis, sound emissions analysis, oil analysis, infrared thermography, and AHP wear particle analysis, all with the overarching goal of identifying the most critical factors. These specified evaluation criteria will play a crucial role as a guiding framework for selecting predictive maintenance techniques, emphasizing simplicity and achieving satisfactory results.

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Hardware Acceleration for Object Detection using YOLOv5 Deep Learning Algorithm on Xilinx Zynq FPGA Platform

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ABSTRACT

Object recognition presents considerable difficulties within the domain of computer vision. Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) offer a flexible hardware platform, having exceptional computing capabilities due to their adaptable topologies, enabling highly parallel, high-performance, and diverse operations that allow for customized reconfiguration of integrated circuits to enhance the effectiveness of object detection accelerators. However, there is a scarcity of assessments that offer a comprehensive analysis of FPGA-based object detection accelerators, and there is currently no comprehensive framework to enable object detection specifically tailored to the unique characteristics of FPGA technology. The You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm is an innovative method that combines speed and accuracy in object detection. This study implemented the YOLOv5 algorithm on a Xilinx® Zynq-7000 System on a Chip (SoC) to perform real-time object detection. Using the MS-COCO dataset, the proposed study showed an

improvement in resource utilization with approximately 42 thousand (78%) look-up tables, 56 thousand (52%) flip-flops, 65 (46%) BRAMs, and 19 (9%) DSPs at a frequency of 250 MHz, improving the effectiveness compared to previous simulated results.

Keywords-object detection; YOLOv5; high level synthesis; FPGA; HDL coder

I. INTRODUCTION

Using state-of-the-art hardware platforms, such as GPUs and FPGAs, has substantially improved deep learning performance in object detection. Several industries find these platforms useful, including video surveillance, industrial design, target tracking, and Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS). Deep learning object identification has been considerably improved by the progress of many techniques, such as the Single-Shot Detector (SSD) [1], the Spatial Pyramid clustering network (SPP-net) [2], and the Region-based Convolutional Neural System [3]. You Only Look Once (YOLO) [4] and Faster R-CNN [5] are two referenced methodological approaches. Among the many effective deep learning techniques, the YOLO approach stands out for its remarkable speed and reliability in object detection [6]. The YOLO method uses a single convolutional neural network to predict the item's confidence level, the likelihood of classes linked to the bounding boxes, and the coordinates of the boxes. Standard Application-Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs) are not very effective in some tasks. As FPGAs use reconfiguration to maximize the adaptability-performance trade-off [7], they are preferred for the execution of deep learning algorithms compared to ASICs and GPUs [7]. This study used YOLO networks to identify objects in the MS-COCO benchmark dataset, which includes a wider variety of categories and occurrences compared to the PASCAL VOC and ImageNet datasets [8]. The MS-COCO dataset consists of photographs showcasing 91 unique item types, with almost 2.5 million accurately annotated instances. This dataset comprises around 10% of a certain category per image, in contrast to the PASCAL VOC and ImageNet benchmark datasets, which encompass 60% of both categories.

Many studies have discussed the design and implementation of FPGAs for deep learning algorithms due to their suitability for this purpose [9-10]. Several FPGA topologies have been proposed for the execution of YOLO algorithms. In [10], the REQ-YOLO framework was proposed, which was specifically designed for object identification and fine-tuned for FPGA implementation and incorporated an innovative Processing Element (PE) arrangement. However, this framework demonstrated an exceptionally high amount of resource utilization. In [11], the rapid Finite Impulse Response (FIR) technique, often known as FFA, was proposed to improve resource use. This technique was specifically designed to efficiently compute CNN models and was successfully implemented on a Xilinx Zynq ZC706. MiniYOLOv3 is an embedded software that has been built and tested using the MS-COCO dataset for real-time applications. In [12], a Multi-Scale Feature Pyramid Network (MSFPN) was specifically built to extract features in a very efficient manner. The design used both group and depth-wise convolution, however, it did not achieve better accuracy and speed than the proposed technique.

In [13], a literature survey was conducted for hardware implementations of visual trackers, highlighting the lack of hardware implementations of state-of-the-art tracking algorithms. In [14], VGG16 was implemented on Xilinx Zynq ZC706 and Virtex VC707 boards, respectively. In [15], the REQ-YOLO was proposed as a resource-aware, systematic weight quantization framework for object detection. In [16], the binary network was combined with a Support Vector Machine (SVM) regression to specifically target lightweight YOLO-v2 using a Xilinx Zynq® Ultrascale+ MPSoC. The use of a shared streaming binarized CNN to sequentially process each layer can effectively decrease the computing complexity of the procedure but does not adequately address the problem of decreasing external memory access. To achieve this objective, a hardware architecture using the VC707 FPGA was introduced in [16] that integrated fast processing capabilities with low power usage, specifically designed for object detection. The resource use for this architecture remained consistently high, regardless of the total efficiency and power. Another limitation was the need to optimize latency, as stated in [12], and the use of a compact YOLOv3 architecture specifically optimized for low-end FPGAs was proposed. Although many FPGA-based hardware solutions have shown the ability to improve CNNs, only a limited number of these systems have extensively studied the complete design process to achieve fast deployment and outstanding power efficiency.

This study proposes the utilization of FPGAs to accelerate the YOLOv5 algorithm, aiming to reduce prediction time while maintaining a high level of accuracy. The YOLOv5 object identification algorithm was accelerated on the Zynq-7000 SoC using efficient resource use, and its performance was compared to other existing approaches. The YOLOv5 algorithm was implemented with hardware acceleration using Vivado 2017.4.

II. YOLO FOR OBJECT DETECTION

The YOLO approach employs the Darknet-53 framework [17] for object detection, which is a cutting-edge algorithm known for its exceptional efficiency and accuracy. The Darknet architecture consists of 53 convolutional layers, which is evident from its name. YOLO v5 has superior speed compared to its predecessors. YOLOv5 employs the Darknet framework as its foundational structure, incorporating YOLOv3 on top. The intermediate layer comprises the Path Aggregation Network (PAN) [18], Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) [19], and the Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) [20]. Figure 1 illustrates the conventional structure of YOLOv5. Extracting features from images involves the deployment of convolutional layers and the use of anchor boxes with a kernel size of $k \times k$ to predict the bounding boxes and perform regression, finally producing a feature map. Additionally, it incorporates pooling layers that are used to sample each input map. A Fully Connected (FC) layer can operate as a classifier. Neural networks use activation functions to enhance their ability to accurately represent data, which is achieved by incorporating layers of nonlinearity. The

activation functions often employed in neural networks include the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), Leaky ReLU, Sigmoid, and Hyperbolic Tangent functions.

YOLO denotes the phrase "You Only Look Once". This study used version 5, a cutting-edge object detection algorithm that currently stands as the most advanced algorithm of its kind. This is a revolutionary CNN that accurately detects objects in real-time. This method uses a singular neural network to analyze the entirety of the image, subsequently segmenting it into distinct components and making predictions on the bounding boxes and probabilities associated with each individual element. The bounding boxes are assigned weights based on the anticipated probability. The "just looks once" method examines the image by making predictions after a single forward propagation pass through the neural network. After performing non-maximum suppression, which guarantees that each object is only identified once, the algorithm presented in Figure 2 proceeds to provide the discovered items.

Fig. 1. YOLOv5 system for object detection.

Fig. 2. The algorithm of the YOLOv5 model.

III. PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

Figure 3 shows the proposed hardware implementation for YOLOv5, illustrating how the Zynq platform can execute the algorithm. Xilinx Programmable Logic (PL) from the 7-series [13], AMBA Interconnects, DDR3 component memory, an ARM Cortex-A9 Processing System (PS), and some peripherals are part of the Zynq™ 7000 XC7Z020-CLG484-1 SoC that was used in the implementation.

Vivado 20.17.4 has a plethora of libraries for the implementation of deep learning algorithms [16]. Deep learning algorithms are implemented using Vivado High-Level Synthesis (HLS) in conjunction with certain Targeted Reference Designs (TRDs) [1]. Each layer is processed sequentially in hardware acceleration. The designer has the option to change the 3x3 kernel size of the CONV layer. When designing the streaming system, it is essential to optimize the timing for each layer. To increase the system throughput in high-level synthesis, loop pipelining is used because of the large amount of incoming data. The Leaky ReLU activation function is used in the network model to solve the gradient vanishing problem [1].

Fig. 3. Proposed architecture of YOLOv5.

A. Design Overview

The YOLOv5 network processes each layer in a specific order, except for the routing layer. It is possible to predetermine the routing layer by providing an address. A memory-data connection is needed for the hardware accelerator to read, process, and write data [2]. By recycling data and tiling the convolution loops, the loop tiling technique optimizes memory access time, which is especially useful for huge amounts of data. When the burst duration exceeds a specific threshold, the effective bandwidth of the FPGA begins to plateau after initially increasing with the burst length. In terms of data layout, the data tiling approach frequently causes DRAM to have non-continuous access. Combining them into a single block, the proposed technique improves the placement of kernel weights inside a tile. This improves effective memory bandwidth by making the most of available external memory bandwidth while reducing the number of memory accesses. Enhancing computational performance through the use of input and output parallelism is crucial for convolutional layer acceleration. Achieving parallelism requires the construction of many parallel addition trees and multiplication units.

Data received from DRAM are distributed to the on-chip buffers by the Data Scatter module, which is also responsible for producing the correct write address. Transferring data from the output buffer back to the DRAM and producing the DRAM write-back address are the two main functions of the Data Gather module. Computations for the Pool, Conv, and Reorg layers, two convolutional layers and one with a Leaky ReLU,

are handled by the pixel buffers. For data translation, the upgraded hardware has one AXI4-Lite slave interface in addition to two AXI4 master interfaces. A link is formed between the weighted buffers and the FC layer using the proposed technique.

B. Hardware Implementation

Several components are part of the proposed FPGA implementation, including an Interrupt Controller, Direct Memory Access (DMA), and General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO). A parameter and processing array, data decoding and rearranging modules, and the PL itself make up the program. The DDR memory in both components is used to connect to the SoC through the Memory Generator Interface, which also carries out the storage of network parameters and mapping of features.

The Deep Learning HDL Toolbox2 in MATLAB R2018b (MathWorks Inc.) is compatible with Xilinx and Intel FPGAs and SoCs for inference purposes. This toolbox allows users to create personalized deep-learning models and assess the performance of hardware implementation. It is feasible to construct and train DL models in MATLAB, as it is also possible to import pre-trained models from different frameworks. The HDL toolkit facilitates the use of 8-bit integer quantization for weight optimization, resulting in enhanced throughput, memory efficiency, power consumption, and computing demands. The DL model can be transformed into portable and synthesizable Verilog or VHDL code using HDL Coder and Simulink. This code can then be deployed on hardware such as FPGA and SoCs. An advantage of this

toolbox is its ability to automatically produce FPGA instructions through the compile command, eliminating the need for human reprogramming. The FPGA can be connected and instructions can be deployed using either the Ethernet or JTAG interface, utilizing the DL processor IP core. When making predictions, it is possible to assess the real-time device performance parameters, such as latency at the layer level, to identify any limitations. The synthesizable Register Transfer Level (RTL) generated by HDL Coder is capable of accommodating various workflows and devices. A customizable IP core that features standard AXI interfaces can be developed for seamless integration into SoCs.

Figure 4 shows the IP core of the MATLAB HDL processor. The toolbox comprises a DL processor with four AXI4 master interfaces, DDR external memory, convolution, FC layer processor, activation normalization, and a controller with scheduling logic. The input data and parameters can be saved in the external DDR memory and then transferred to the block RAM via one of the AXI4 master interfaces. The block RAM supplies activations to the general convolution and fully connected processor. The convolution and FC processor execute the convolution operation and compute the FC layers. The activation normalization module is responsible for including the ReLU nonlinearity, a max-pooling layer, or executing Local Response Normalization (LRN). The IP core consists of two controllers: one for the convolution and another for the FC layer. The generic convolution/fully connected processor with activation normalization can process only one layer sequentially. The subsequent layer undergoes processing through the controller, specifically in terms of scheduling.

Fig. 4. HDL coder proposal for object detection on Zynq7000.

Fig. 5. RTL design for YOLOv5 for object detection Vivado project.

The processing phase involves sending PL configuration instructions via GPIO after ARM executes them for each layer. Control signals are transmitted to the relevant units based on decoded instructions. The original picture is retrieved from the Programmable SoC Direct Read (PSDDR) module and transmitted to the PL module by the Direct Memory Access (DMA) module. Before transmission to the processing array, the pixels are rearranged by the input data reordering module. The PL-DDR provides the DDR controller in PL with the model parameters, which are then stored in the parameters buffer.

The Processing Array (PA) receives its parameters from the parameter buffer. Processing Elements (PEs) are used to construct PAs to facilitate concurrent processing. These components of parallel processing perform calculations for several output channels using the same input feature maps. These parallel processing components use the same input feature mappings to compute for a large number of output channels. At the same time, the PEs complete the computations for each layer. The next step is for the PS-DDR to help get the feature maps from the last layer back to the host PC. To obtain the object detection results, the host PC uses the final feature maps to run Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS).

Resource availability and data interdependence in the design are the limiting factors in the achieved data transmission rate. Figure 5 shows the proposed implementation of Zynq-SoC-based real-time object detection. The proposed approach uses more BRAMs, therefore, it can be implemented with a suitable data processing rate and great efficiency for object detection in real-time. Table I shows a qualitative example of hardware acceleration using the MS-COCO dataset in the proposed system for object detection. The proposed YOLOv5-SOC can achieve an overall performance of 120 fps while effectively predicting different types of items.

TABLE I. RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND MAXIMUM FREQUENCY FOR THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Xilinx platform	Zynq 7020
Maximum frequency	250 Mhz
LUTs	42025 (78.99%)
Flip flops	56141 (52.76)
BRAMs	65.50 (46.79%)
DSPs	19 (8.64%)

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to enhance the performance of object detection by developing a reconfigurable architecture. The YOLOv5 algorithm for object detection was implemented with hardware acceleration on the Zynq SoC. The MS-COCO benchmark dataset was used to evaluate the YOLOv5 algorithm for object detection when executed with hardware acceleration on the Zynq SoC. The Vivado HLS tool was used to synthesize and implement an object detection algorithm on an SoC. This implementation achieves superior resource efficiency, with 78% of Look-Up Tables (LUTs), 52% of Flip-Flops, 42% of Block RAMs (BRAMs), and 8.4% of Digital Signal Processors (DSPs) being utilized. These results were compared with previous implementations. The proposed acceleration achieved a performance of 120 fps at a 250 MHz frequency while minimizing power consumption and effectively utilizing resources. The results demonstrate that the implementation of the YOLOv5 algorithm on FPGA hardware yields a performance that is twice as efficient, with significantly reduced prediction time. FPGAs are well-suited for implementing intricate algorithms, while their primary negative is the extensive time required for development. Despite the development of new tools, reconfiguration of FPGAs remains a tough task.

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Optimal Valley-Filling Algorithm for Electric Two-wheeler Charging Stations

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ABSTRACT

In Vietnam, comprehensive measures are required to accommodate and encourage the potential development of electric two-wheelers in urban traffic and the rooftop solar power potential. In the case of PV-integrated electric two-wheeler charging stations, numerous vehicles charging simultaneously may trigger very high peak loads which adversely impacts other loads and the distribution grid. In this study, an optimal valley-filling algorithm for electric two-wheeler charging stations is proposed. The proposed algorithm can update the variation of available vehicles as well as the dynamic changes in the energy level of individual E2Ws at each time slot. The simulation results proved that the proposed method can effectively perform valley filling, significantly improving the total load profile compared to uncontrolled charging and average charging schemes.

Keywords-electric two-wheelers; charging station; valley-filling; solar power; charging algorithms

I. INTRODUCTION

It has been shown that the utilization of renewable energy, especially rooftop photovoltaic (PV) power, for Electric Vehicle (EV) charging contributes to achieving multiple objectives such as: (1) meeting the charging demand while reducing adverse impacts of charging loads on the distribution grid, (2) encouraging self-generation-self-consumption and mitigating negative impacts of high PV penetration rate into the distribution grid, (3) reducing the need for grid upgradation, and (4) reducing greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Furthermore, in developing countries like Vietnam, electric two-wheelers (E2Ws) are considered suitable for the existing transport infrastructure and socio-economic conditions [2, 3]. However, the transition from fossil fuel motorcycles to E2Ws requires appropriate and comprehensive measures regarding infrastructure planning and charging solutions for this type of vehicle. Uncontrolled EV charging may increase peak load and energy losses and trigger inefficient system operation [4]. If charging stations are located in offices, apartment buildings, factories etc., uncontrolled charging could result in very high peak loads, because the arrival and departure of vehicles usually concentrate on certain times and vehicles tend to be charged at their maximum permitted rate as soon as they are connected.

Regarding load shifting and valley filling solutions, numerous approaches have been proposed such as broadcasting charging tariffs with different rates depending on total load

level [5], leveraging quadratic programming [6], leveraging linear programming and receding horizon control [7]. However, these studies only focus on electric car charging infrastructure instead of E2W charging stations. The research on improving load profile for E2W charging stations is still limited. Although charging power and battery capacity of E2Ws is negligible compared to electric cars, hundreds of E2Ws charging simultaneously can result in a very high peak load. In addition, scheduling numerous vehicles requires appropriate approaches regarding architecture and scheduling algorithms.

Several works have conducted research on the E2W charging station feasibility [1, 3], E2W charging station architecture [8], and scheduling algorithms for E2W charging stations in Vietnam [9, 10]. However, these works have not addressed the uncertainties regarding the arrival and departure of vehicles. Thus, this study proposes an algorithm that dynamically updates both the availability of vehicles at each timeslot and the change in energy level of vehicle batteries.

The main contributions of this work are: (1) a valley-filling algorithm for PV-integrated E2W charging stations is proposed, (2) the algorithm is able to update the variation of available E2Ws and energy levels of vehicles, (3) by adopting the algorithm, PV utilization for charging is proved to be more efficient, (4) the algorithm contributes to adverse impact mitigation of EV charging and PV on other loads and on the distribution grid.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND THE PROPOSED ALGORITHM

A. Objective Function

Most studies consider charging problems being scheduled in a day or a scheduling horizon which is usually discretized into 96 timeslots of 15 minutes [11]. For the load profile improving problem, the optimization objective aims to minimize the load fluctuation. This can be interpreted as total load variance minimization. Thus, the objective function would be as in (1):

$$\min F_{obj} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{t=1}^M (D_S^t + \sum_{i=1}^N P_i^t - \mu_{ave}^S)^2 \quad (1)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N P_i^t \leq \min\{\sum_{i=1}^N P_{cmax_i}, \sum_{i=1}^N P_{bmax_i}\} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N P_i^t \leq P_{feedermax} - D_S(t) \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N A_i (FSOC_{EVi} - ISOC_{EVi}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\int_{t_0}^{t_m} \eta_i P_i(t) \right) \quad (4)$$

where M is the total timeslot number of the scheduling horizon, D_S^t (also known as netload) is the total power of non-EV loads subtracting the power generated by the PV system at time t , N is the total number of E2Ws been serviced during the scheduling horizon, P_i^t represents the charging power of E2W $_i$ at timeslot t , η_i is the charging efficiency of E2W $_i$, P_{cmax_i} is the maximum allowable charging power for the i^{th} charger, P_{bmax_i} is the maximum allowable charging power for the battery of the E2W $_i$, $P_{feedermax}$ represents the maximum allowable exchange power between the microgrid and the distribution grid, A_i is the battery capacity of E2W $_i$, $FSOC_{EVi}$ is the State of Charge (SoC) of E2W $_i$ at the departure time, $ISOC_{EVi}$ is the initial SoC of E2W $_i$, and μ_{ave}^S represents the average power of total load during the scheduling horizon which is expressed as in (5):

$$\mu_{ave}^S = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{t=1}^M (D_S^t + \sum_{i=1}^N P_i^t) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{t=1}^M D_S^t + \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{A_i (FSOC_{EVi} - ISOC_{EVi})}{\eta_i \cdot M \cdot \Delta T} \quad (5)$$

Constraint (2) shows that at any timeslot, total charging power of all E2Ws in the charging station cannot exceed the maximum allowable of all chargers and batteries. Besides, it also must not exceed the supply capacity of the grid as in constraint (3). Constraint (4) is the energy requirement constraint. This constraint assures that at the departure time, E2Ws reach their required SoC level. Considering the E2Ws individually, the following constraints should be met:

$$A_i (FSOC_{EVi} - ISOC_{EVi}) = \int_{t_0}^{t_m} \eta_i \cdot P_i(t) \quad (6)$$

$$P_i^t \leq \min\{P_{cmax_i}, P_{bmax_i}\} \quad (7)$$

$$A_i \cdot ISOC_{EVi} + \int_{t_0}^{t_m} \eta_i \cdot P_i(t) \leq A_i \quad (8)$$

$$A_i \cdot ISOC_{EVi} + \int_{t_0}^{t_m} \eta_i \cdot P_i(t) \geq A_i \cdot (1 - DOD_{max}^{EVi}) \quad (9)$$

where DOD_{max}^{EVi} is the maximum depth of discharge of an E2W $_i$. Constraint (6) is the required energy constraint.

Charging power at timeslots must satisfy (7). Constraint (8) is the maximum battery capacity constraint while depth of discharge constraint is as in (9).

B. Real-Time Update and Algorithm Proposition

To address the issue of arrival/departure uncertainty, the charging station must update the available E2Ws, including the existing E2Ws and any new E2W arrival/departure. It is assumed that the charging station is able to recognize the nominal capacity of the onboard battery, the battery SoC [12], and the maximum permitted charging power via a Vehicle Information System (VIS) which is responsible for providing E2W information to the station controller [13]. After communicating with the VIS and E2W owners, scheduling data are updated depending on the new arrivals and departures. The proposed algorithm can be summarized in the following steps:

- Step 1: Considering the current timeslot, the charging station dynamically updates the E2Ws connected to the station, including newly arriving E2Ws and departing E2Ws. Current SoC measurement data must also be acquired.
- Step 2: Finding the charging pattern of E2Ws by solving the objective function.
- Step 3: Applying the charging pattern to the E2Ws at the current timeslot.

After the three steps, in the next timeslot, the process of updating, finding charging patterns, and applying charging patterns repeats until the end of the scheduling horizon.

III. CASE STUDY AND SIMULATION RESULTS

This study assumes that the forecast data of solar generation and conventional load are available and sufficiently accurate. The charging station is assumed to be in Vietnam, servicing up to 250 vehicles in each working shift. A working day consists of two shifts: the morning shift is from 7:30 to 15:00 and the afternoon shift is from 14:30 to 21:00. The E2W batteries have a capacity of 1,200 Wh. Maximum charging/discharging powers are 400/400 W, respectively. Batteries are not allowed to discharge if the SoC is less than 20%. At the end of the working shift, the E2W batteries are full. For the purpose of investigating the performance of the proposed algorithm, this case study does not investigate the variation in the non-EV load profile as well as PV generation in different days or different seasons. Sets of these data are generated and used as the input data for the algorithm.

A. Data of Initial SoC

With 250 E2Ws per working shift, the data of the initial SoC of the E2Ws in this case study are generated based on the research results of [14]. The vehicles have the initial SoCs shown in Table I.

B. Arrival/Departure Behavior

Numerous studies have shown that the probability distribution of arrival and departure time could be statistically modeled with proper probability density functions like the normal distribution function [1, 15].

TABLE I. INITIAL SoC OF E2Ws

Initial SoC	E2W Number	Initial SoC	E2W Number
90 – 100%	29	40 – 50%	28
80 – 90%	37	30 – 40%	21
70 – 80%	37	20 – 30%	15
60 – 70%	37	10 – 20%	8
50 – 60%	35	0 – 10%	3

Thus, in this study, patterns of arrival/departure which follow a normal distribution function, are generated. The probability distribution parameters are:

- Morning arrival time: mean: 7.25, deviation: 0.12.
- Morning departure time: mean: 14.75, deviation: 0.12.
- Afternoon arrival time: mean: 14.25, deviation: 0.12.
- Afternoon departure time: mean: 20.75, deviation: 0.12.

Arrival/departure patterns are used as input for algorithm verification.

C. PV Power Output

In this case study, a 225 kWp solar system is simulated based on weather data in Hanoi, Vietnam. The system consists of 542 PV panels. Each panel has a power rating of 415 Wp. The PV power outputs of a typical day in January (month with the lowest solar irradiance) and in June (the highest solar irradiance month) are simulated as in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. PV power output in January and in June.

Because sufficiently accurate solar power data are assumed to be available, this study only utilizes simulation results of the PV system as input data for the proposed algorithm. Thus, the variation in solar power output in different days and different seasons is not considered in this work.

D. Non-EV Load

For the purpose of algorithm verification, conventional load data are retrieved from the dataset in [16]. The non-EV load profile is shown in Figure 2. It should be noted that for a two-shift commercial center, a relatively flat profile occurs during working hours. Conventional load reaches its valley in the early morning and rapidly increases when the morning shift starts. However, in the case of solar power participation, solar power can partially supply load, triggering a more fluctuating netload curve.

Fig. 2. Non-EV load profile.

Fig. 3. Netload profile.

Figure 3 shows the netload profile in January and in June, respectively. In January, the minimum netload value is 82,967 W at 12:00 and the maximum is 1.84 times higher at 18:00. In June, due to the high PV power output, the netload profile is more fluctuating. The maximum netload value is 151,647 W (at 19:00) which is 3.89 times higher than the minimum netload of 38,967 W at noon.

E. Simulation Results

In this work, several operation scenarios are proposed and analyzed to investigate the algorithm’s effectiveness. Because battery wear and tear cost may be a crucial barrier, this work does not consider the Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) feature. Hence, the case study includes the following operation scenarios:

- Scenario 1: Charging load does not participate in the microgrid. This scenario is analyzed to evaluate netload variation in the case of solar power participation.
- Scenario 2: Average charging: The E2Ws are charged at constant rate to reach their required SoC at their departure time.
- Scenario 3: Uncontrolled charging: The E2Ws are charged at the maximum allowable power as soon as they are connected to the station.
- Scenario 4: Smart charging: The E2Ws follow the proposed algorithm.

Figure 4 depicts the total load profile of the four scenarios in a typical day in January.

Fig. 4. Total load profile in the considered scenarios.

Considering time, when the E2Ws are available at the charging station, in January, the peak conventional load is 152,467 W at 10:00 AM. This value is 1.05 times higher than the lowest value of 145,333 W at 21:00. However, when solar power participates in the system, the peak netload of 152,300 W (at 18:00) is 1.84 times higher than the lowest netload of 82,967 W (at 12:00). Thus, solar power participation deteriorates the total load profile, triggering a more fluctuating curve. In scenario 2, because E2Ws are charged at constant rates, the total load profile remains almost the same as in scenario 1. However, in arrival/departure periods, because E2Ws connect/disconnect to the station at different time, total charging power will gradually increase/decrease (Figure 5). Thus, the shape of aggregated load would be different compared to scenario 1. In addition, 250 E2Ws servicing per shift results in around 14,690 W higher total power consumption than that of scenario 1.

Generally, the average charging scheme manages to evenly distribute the charging power during parking time (Figure 5). Thus, it does not significantly impact the total load profile. However, during the shift transition time (from 14:30 to 15:00), the average charging scenario produces a high total charging power (Figure 5), because the vehicles from the previous shift have not left the charging station yet, while the vehicles of the next shift have arrived, resulting in a large number of E2W charging simultaneously at the shift transition period.

Under scenario 3, because E2Ws are charged at their maximum permitted rate as soon as they are connected to the station, total load reaches very high peaks at arrival times. To be specific, the first peak of 223,308 W occurs at 7:30 and the second peak of 195,435 W is at 14:30. After reaching the peaks, total charging power declines swiftly because E2Ws stop charging when their energy requirements are met (Figure 5). Thus, after several timeslots, the total load gets back to the netload. Uncoordinated charging triggers the worst load profile. The peak load is 223,308 W, being 2.69 times higher than the base load of 82,967 W. The total load profile shows a dramatical improvement under the proposed smart charging strategy. E2Ws are charged at low load periods and avoid increasing peak load. Compared to the other scenarios, this scheme produces the flattest aggregated load profile. Valley filling effect is clearly demonstrated. Furthermore, because valley load time coincides with high PV generation time, the E2W charging power profile is quite consistent with the PV power output, implying that the smart charging scheme can utilize solar power for charging more effectively. Charging profiles and battery capacity profiles of several E2Ws in January and in June are illustrated as in Figures 6-11. These E2W are representatives of high, medium, and low initial SoC as show in Table II.

Fig. 5. Total charging power profiles.

Fig. 6. Profiles of E2W1.

Fig. 7. Profile of E2W141.

Fig. 8. Profile of E2W247.

Fig. 9. Profiles of E2W251.

Fig. 10. Profiles of E2W391.

Fig. 11. Profiles of E2W497.

TABLE II. HIGH, MEDIUM, AND LOW SoC E2W REPRESENTATIVES

Shift	Initial SoC	E2W ID
Morning	90 – 100%	1
	50 – 60%	141
	10 – 20%	247
Afternoon	90 – 100%	251
	50 – 60%	391
	10 – 20%	497

Simulation results reveal that E2Ws of the morning shift tend to charge from 10:00 to 13:30 while E2Ws of the afternoon shift perform charging from 14:15 to 16:30. This time also corresponds to the periods of highest solar power. In June, the abundance of solar power results in a lower netload valley than in January. Thus, the valley filling algorithm will schedule vehicles to be charged at higher rates. As a consequence, charging processes in June end earlier than in months with lower solar generation.

Considering E2Ws with different initial SoCs, the lower ones (E2W_ID247; E2W_ID497) are charged at higher speed

than the higher ones (E2W_ID141; E2W_ID1; E2W_ID391; E2W_ID251). Simulation results also show that all charging processes end before departure time and all E2Ws reach their energy requirements.

IV. CONCLUSION

The participation of solar power into energy systems may deteriorate the total load profile if PV power output is not consistent with conventional load profile. Smart charging scheduling may offer an effective solution for improving aggregated load profile. Thus, it can contribute to mitigating adverse impacts of high PV penetration rate and emerging charging load on the energy systems.

In the context of Vietnam, E2Ws emerge as a promising alternative for gasoline-powered motorcycles. In the case of numerous E2Ws implement charging simultaneously such as charging in parking of factories, office buildings, commercial centers, apartments etc., solutions addressing high aggregated charging load, effectively scheduling, load shifting, and valley filling would become imperative.

This study proposes a valley filling algorithm for PV-integrated E2W charging stations. When current timeslot changes, the station controller would update arrival/departure events, update new energy level of available vehicles then implement scheduling. The process of updating, finding charging patterns and applying charging patterns repeats until the end of the scheduling horizon.

Simulation results show that, compared to uncontrolled charging and average charging schemes, the proposed algorithm proves its effectiveness in valley filling. E2Ws are scheduled to be charged at valley load time, effectively leveraging the flexibility of charging load and at the same time, can indirectly lesser adverse impacts of PV sources and E2W on the distribution grid.

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Design and Implementation of an IoT-based automated EC and pH Control System in an NFT-based Hydroponic Farm

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ABSTRACT

In hydroponics, the growth of plants is primarily dependent on the precise configuration of the nutrient solution supplied to them. Continuous monitoring and control of the nutrients in the hydroponic tank is essential to maintain optimal growth requirements at all times. Manual monitoring and control of the system is inefficient, as it requires human intervention and can lead to errors and variations in the nutrients supplied. This study presents a system to automatically track pH, current nutrient, and water level in the tank and supply the exact amount of pH solution, nutrient solution, and water whenever needed. The proposed system, when integrated with IoT technology, can help achieve better control over the farm and higher productivity with a reduced amount of manual labor.

Keywords-nutrient control; dosing system; hydroponic; automation; internet of things; EC; pH

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydroponics is a farming technique that is based on the cultivation of hydroculture plants [1]. In this technique, plants are grown in a water medium, without soil, and all the required mineral nutrients are supplied through the water. Various factors affect plant growth and crop quality in a hydroponic setup, such as pH levels, concentration, and Electrical Conductivity (EC) of the nutrient solution. The pH is an indicator of the acid or alkaline levels of the solution. Each nutrient in the feeding solution responds differently to changes in the pH level of the solution, and thus plant productivity is directly dependent on pH regulation. The concentration of the nutrient-rich solution depends on two factors: the concentration of the solution, expressed as Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) and the conductivity value of the solution stated as EC [2]. TDS represents the combined amount of all organic and inorganic substances present in a liquid, and the EC is the amount of salts present in the liquid. This dissolved salt in the form of cations and anions makes the nutrient solution electrically conductive [2]. The more nutrients present in the water, the higher the concentration, leading to a higher EC and vice versa. Every plant has an ideal EC that is crucial for its growth, and the inability to maintain the EC in the vital optimal range in the nutrient solution adversely affects its growth [3]. Therefore, maintaining the optimal nutrient density in the solution is a

critical aspect and is possible by keeping the EC at the ideal level depending on the type of plant being cultivated.

This study presents an algorithm for the automated monitoring and control of the nutrient dosing system for a hydroponic farm by maintaining nutrient solution parameters (pH and EC) throughout the plant growth life cycle with minimal human intervention [4-5]. Similar studies have already been carried out in the field of automated EC and pH control. In [2], fuzzy logic was used to keep EC in the desired range of 1.0-1.5 mS/cm in a hydroponic system based on the nutrient film technique. This method takes the ideal EC value, the current EC value, and the water level as inputs and provides the time duration for which the water or nutrient valves should be turned on. The algorithm was supported by an Android application to remotely control and monitor the hydroponic plants. In [6], a smart irrigation and nutrient supply system was designed by implementing a fuzzy logic controller to maintain the flow of water and acid and basic solutions in the soil to balance its pH and moisture levels. A mobile application was designed to store and display system data. This system was tested on a chili farm and the results showed that plant growth improved compared to an uncontrolled growth medium. In [7], fuzzy logic control was used to design a hydroponic system built on NFT. The image processing of the HSV histogram was applied to predict the ideal EC for the growth cycle of plants. The system was tested in a pakchoy mustard plant and the

results showed that it was capable of predicting nutrient levels in agreement with the age of the plant with a fault rate of 8.9%. In [8], a nutrition feeding system was proposed using an Arduino UNO R3 board. This system used the GP2Y0A21 proximity sensors to detect the water level of the feeding tank and a TDS sensor to detect EC levels. The system was successfully tested on a prototype scale to keep the water levels in the tank at the optimal level and feed nutrients when the concentration fell below 800 ppm.

As there is no single solution to automate both EC and pH in a hydroponic farm, this study developed a combined algorithm to continuously maintain the EC and pH levels in an NFT hydroponic farm. In addition, most studies did not consider the effect of various kinds of water, such as natural, distilled, or fresh water, on the TDS and EC ratio while automating them in the nutrient solution. This study aimed to evaluate the correlation of TDS and EC for different types of water to simultaneously maintain and monitor them at all times. Furthermore, the prevailing automation algorithms do not consider the total volume of the tank and the current volume of the nutrient solution when deciding to add more water, nutrient solution, or pH solution to manipulate EC and pH. The proposed algorithm uses the size of the nutrient tank as user input from the app, and the current volume of the solution is constantly monitored using an ultrasonic sensor to ensure its effectiveness for farms with variable nutrient tank sizes.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

Figure 1 presents the design of the proposed IoT-based hydroponic system with automated EC and pH control. The system contains a NodeMCU microcontroller that executes the proposed algorithm for automated maintenance and control of EC and pH values. NodeMCU receives current data from the ultrasonic, TDS, and pH sensors connected to the hydroponic system and decides, based on the values received, whether any manipulation is necessary for the water level, nutrient density, or pH value of the water in the irrigation tank [9]. For instance, if the optimal pH level of the farm is set between 6 and 7 and at any given time the pH sensor reads the water pH level at 10, then the microcontroller decides that the pH-lowering solution needs to be added to the irrigation tank to bring it to the ideal range.

Fig. 1. System design.

The automation system calculates the time duration for which the pump attached to the pH-down solution needs to be turned on, and the same signal will be sent to the relay module to switch on pump 4 for the stipulated period. During this period, the pH-lowering solution from the respective tank will be added to the main irrigation tank of the hydroponic NFT system, thus automatically controlling the pH of the water [10]. In the same way, this system can maintain the nutrient concentration of the irrigation tank by adding more nutrient solution if EC levels fall below the ideal range or by adding more water if EC exceeds the ideal range. The algorithms for deciding and calculating the pump-on duration are discussed in the following section [9, 11-12].

III. AUTOMATION ALGORITHM ON NFT

Maintaining and automatically controlling the nutrient dosing system in an NFT hydroponic farm with minimum human intervention requires automation of two important parameters of the nutrient solution, namely the nutrient density and the pH level of the nutrient solution. Figure 2 shows a diagram of the parameters elaborated below.

Fig. 2. Design of automated EC and pH control.

A. Nutrient Density

The density of the nutrients in the water flowing through the NFT system depends on EC and TDS. A higher EC value represents a higher concentration of dissolved nutrients in the water. These two parameters are correlated, and the association is expressed by [13]:

$$TDS \left(\frac{mg}{L} \right) = X * EC \left(\frac{mS}{cm} \right) \tag{1}$$

where X is the concentration of charged atoms in water and is therefore dependent on the salinity (EC) of the water. Table I displays the association of EC and TDS in water of different salinity [13]:

TABLE I. CORRELATION OF EC AND TDS IN WATER OF DIFFERENT SALINITY [6]

Water Type	EC (Measured at 25 °C)	Ratio TDS/EC (X value)
Natural Water	500 – 3,000 μS/cm	0.55 – 0.75
Distilled Water	1 – 10 μS/cm	0.5
Fresh Water	300 – 800 μS/cm	0.55

This study uses fresh water with EC in the range of 300 to 350 μS/cm for irrigation in the NFT hydroponic farm. Accordingly, the value of X is assumed to be 0.550.

To maintain nutrient density in the ideal range, the system adds more nutrients when TDS falls below the lower bound and adds more water if TDS exceeds the upper bound of the optimal range. The automated TDS control system needs two parameters from the NFT system: the current TDS of the nutrient water in the irrigation tank and the current volume of the irrigation tank. The first parameter is obtained through the TDS sensor attached to the system and the second parameter is obtained by the following equation:

$$V_{Current} = V_{Tank} * \frac{H_{Tank} - ULT_{Sensor}}{H_{Tank}} \quad (2)$$

where $V_{Current}$ is the current level of nutrient water in the irrigation tank, V_{Tank} is the total volume of the tank, H_{Tank} is the height of the irrigation tank and ULT_{Sensor} is the input reading obtained from the ultrasonic sensor attached to the irrigation tank. If the current TDS is less than the lower limit of the optimal range required for plant growth, (3) is applied to calculate the amount of concentrated nutrient solution to be added to the irrigation tank to balance the TDS levels. If the current TDS is greater than the upper limit of the optimal range, then (4) is used to calculate the volume of water to be added to the irrigation tank.

$$V_{Nutrient} = \frac{TT - CT}{NT - TT} * V_{Current} \quad (3)$$

$$V_{Water} = \frac{CT - CT}{TT} * V_{Current} \quad (4)$$

where $V_{Nutrient}$ is the volume of concentrated nutrient solution to be added to the tank, V_{Water} is the volume of water to be added to the tank, TT is the target TDS to be achieved, which is the average of the ideal TDS range, CT is the current TDS obtained from the TDS sensor, NT is the TDS of the concentrated nutrient solution, and $V_{Current}$ is the water level obtained from (2). After obtaining the volume of either nutrients or water to be added, the last step in the EC maintenance algorithm is to send a signal to the relay to turn on pump 1 in case of water and pump 2 in case of nutrients should be added. The duration in which pump 2 remains open to add nutrients to the irrigation tank is calculated using (5), and the duration for pump 1 to open to add water to the irrigation tank is calculated using (6).

$$Duration_N = \frac{V_{Nutrient}}{FL} * 60 \quad (5)$$

$$Duration_W = \frac{V_{Water}}{FL} * 60 \quad (6)$$

where $Duration_W$ is the amount of time (s) the pump 1 connected to the water will open, $Duration_N$ is the amount of time (s) pump 2, connected to the nutrient solution, will open, $V_{Nutrient}$ and V_{Water} are the volumes obtained from (3) or (4) and FL is the flow rate of the pump in ml/s.

B. pH Level

Two types of pH solutions were used to maintain the pH level in the required range: an acidic solution of pH 3 and a basic solution of pH 9.5. To automate the process of maintaining pH, the system needs the recommended doses of the acidic and basic solutions as input from the user. The concentrated solutions are then diluted by a factor of 10 and stored in separate tanks to maintain the pH of the nutrient tank. The system regularly takes readings from the pH sensor

installed in the nutrient water and compares the input value with the ideal range required. When the sensor reading is less than the ideal range, the basic (pH-up) solution is added to the nutrient water, and when the reading is greater than the upper bound of the optimal range, the acidic (pH-down) solution is added to the tank. The amount of acidic or basic solution to be added is calculated using (7). Next, based on the dose, the system calculates the pump-on duration to add the calculated dose to the nutrient tank using (8).

$$R_V = V_{Current} * R_{rec} * 10 \quad (7)$$

$$Duration_{pH} = \frac{R_V}{FL_{pH}} \quad (8)$$

where R_{rec} is the recommended dose of the pH-up and pH-down solutions in 1 liter of water recommended by the manufacturer and given as an input to the system by the user, R_V is the calculated dose of pH-up and pH-down solutions according to the current volume ($V_{Current}$) of the nutrient tank (recommended doses are diluted by the ration of 10 to 1), $Duration_{pH}$ is the duration of time in seconds for which the pump connected to the respective pH solution should be turned on and FL_{pH} is the flow rate of the pumps connected to the pH solutions.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

The above automated EC and pH control and maintenance design was implemented through the experimental setup shown in Figure 1 on a small-scale indoor hydroponic NFT system consisting of an irrigation tank for nutrient supply, water for NFT in tank 1 with pump 1 connected to it, concentrated nutrient solution in tank 2 with pump 2 connected to it, and pH-up and pH-down solutions in tanks 3 and 4 with pumps 3 and 4 connected to them, respectively. The automation algorithm was implemented in the system and Tables II and III show the experimental results of EC and pH, respectively, taken at random times throughout the day. The results show that the proposed algorithm was able to detect current TDS and pH values and take the required action when the parameters were not in the optimal range. For example, if the pH of the needed irrigation tank is 5.93, which is less than the minimum pH as given by the user, the algorithm turns on the pump connected to the basic solution needs. The relay connected to the required pump was turned on for 11.45 s, which was calculated based on the current pH and the volume of the tank, resulting in a pH value of 6.12 which is in the optimal range.

TABLE II. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF EC CONTROL

INPUTS: Ideal TDS range =750-850 ppm, TT = 800 ppm, H _{Tank} = 50 cm, V _{Tank} = 50 l, FLN = 0.6 l/min, NT = 2000 ppm				
V _{current} (l)	Current TDS (CT)	Action needed	Pump ON time (Duration _N)	Resulting TDS (TT)
45.0	745	Nutrient pump ON	206.25 s	792
43.2	853	Water pump ON	286.2 s	801
46.7	774	No action needed	N/A	N/A
44.5	851	Water pump ON	283.7 s	798
45.3	824	No action needed	N/A	N/A
43.8	748	Nutrient pump ON	189.8 s	796
47.4	797	No action needed	N/A	N/A
47	856	Water pump ON	329 s	832
49.2	743	Nutrient pump ON	233.7 s	784
42.6	853	Water pump ON	282.2 s	821

TABLE III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF PH CONTROL

INPUTS: Ideal pH range = 6-6.5, $H_{tank} = 50$ cm, $FL_{pH} = 0.6$ l/min				
$V_{current}$ (l)	Current pH (C_{pH})	Action needed	Pump ON time ($Duration_{pH}$)	Resulting pH (T_{pH})
46.2	5.96	pH-up pump ON	11.55 sec	6.12
43.9	6.3	No action needed	N/A	N/A
45.8	5.93	pH-up pump ON	11.45 sec	6.09
44.7	6.51	pH-down pump ON	11.175 sec	6.36
44.0	6.57	pH-down pump ON	11 sec	6.41
47.3	6.42	No action needed	N/A	N/A
43.5	5.76	pH-up pump ON	10.875 sec	6.15
48	6.67	pH-down pump ON	12 sec	6.37
44.2	5.93	pH-up pump ON	11.05	6.09
47.84	6.32	No action needed	N/A	N/A

V. RESULT ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

An efficient automation algorithm is instrumental for a successful hydroponic farm, as manually maintaining farm parameters is a tedious task that can result in errors that can negatively affect crop production. Automation of the EC, TDS, and pH levels of the farm ensures that the NFT system always passes an adequate amount of nutrients to the plant, eliminating human errors. This study proposed an automation algorithm that considers the various types of water used to make nutrient solutions, maintains the EC and pH levels simultaneously without the need for human intervention, and considers the total size of the nutrient tank that allows its implementation farms of different sizes. The algorithm was then applied to a small-scale NFT hydroponic farm on a test-case basis for 10 days, and all farm parameters for nutrient control were examined through the installed sensors. The ideal TDS and pH ranges were taken from the user through a mobile app. In the case study to test the algorithm, the ideal TDS range was set to 750-850 ppm and the ideal pH range was 6.0-6.5 by the user. The system was able to maintain the resulting TDS level (TT) at an average of 801.4 ppm and the resulting pH level (T_{pH}) at an average of 6.26 for the duration of the case study, both within the required range. Furthermore, the proposed system can be implemented in other types of precision agriculture, such as aquaponics or aeroponics, with minimal changes.

VI. CONCLUSION

The EC and pH values of a hydroponic system must be in the ideal range to ensure optimal nutrient absorption and plant growth. Maintaining these parameters in the ideal range at all times requires continuous sensing and precision, as the longer the parameters deviate from the range, the lower the nutrient absorption in plants. Manually sensing and adjusting values needs regular human intervention. An automation algorithm that is capable of sensing parameters at regular intervals and automatically acting to keep them in the ideal range is important for hydroponic farms to produce good-quality crops. The proposed system detects TDS and pH levels through sensors, chooses the action that should be taken if the parameters are not in the required range, calculates the duration for which the action will take place, and finally implements it to bring the parameters in the ideal range. Compared to manual monitoring and control, the proposed automation system is more reliable as it significantly reduces the chances of human error and the need for persistent human support.

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Subgrade Reaction Characteristics to the Anchor Pile of a Sheet Pile Quay Wall

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ABSTRACT

The Conventional Design Method (CDM) for anchored sheet pile quay walls cannot accurately calculate the anchor pile deformation, partly because it does not properly consider the subgrade reaction. This study aims to clarify the subgrade reaction characteristics to the anchor pile using finite element analysis. The CDM assumes that passive failure occurs at the front of the anchor pile. On the contrary, this study shows that the active failure region generated from the back of the sheet pile wall expands to the periphery of the anchor pile and the passive failure region is not generated at its front. Thus, the subgrade reaction to the anchor pile is found to be smaller than the CDM assumption. The CDM also neglects the subgrade reaction in parts shallower than the tie-rod mounting height in the pile front. This study clarifies that the subgrade reaction in this part greatly contributes to the deformation resistance of the pile. Consequently, the subgrade reaction in the shallower range than the tie-rod mounting height is greater than or equal to that in the deeper range. Furthermore, the subgrade reaction has a lower upper limit when acting on the anchor pile than when acting on a horizontally stratified ground, and the difference between these limits widens as the reference earthquake strengthens.

Keywords-sheet pile quay wall; seismic resistant design; subgrade reaction; anchor pile; active failure

I. INTRODUCTION

Quay walls are essential port facilities for cargo handling. During an earthquake, quay walls can deform even if their structural members are sound, causing serviceability problems [1-3]. The amount of deformation should be assessed in the seismic design of quay walls [4-6]. In an anchored sheet pile quay wall, the sheet pile wall and the anchor pile are combined by a tie-rod. As the tie-rod is very stiff, its elongation during an earthquake is negligible, and the deformation at the crown height of the sheet pile quay wall coincides with that of the anchor pile. In this scenario, the deformation of the anchor pile must be calculated accurately.

The deformation of the anchor pile during an earthquake is greatly influenced by its interaction with the ground. Various methods have been proposed to simply evaluate the deformation of anchor piles during earthquakes based on the assumption that the ground deforms as a rigid body block [7-9]. However, these methods cannot calculate the amount of deformation with good accuracy due to insufficient consideration of the interaction between the anchor pile and the ground. The Conventional Design Method (CDM) [5] uses the beam-on-Winkler-foundation method, which considers the interaction between the anchor pile and the ground to calculate

its deformation during earthquakes. However, the CDM cannot also accurately evaluate the deformation of the anchor pile during an earthquake for two reasons [10]. First, the anchor pile is subjected to translation, rotation, and bending deformations during an earthquake, whereas the CDM assumes that the anchor pile is not deformed below a certain depth, at which it is strongly confined and deformed only by bending at shallower depths. In practice, the ground behind the sheet pile wall is not horizontally stratified and experiences shear stress prior to the occurrence of the earthquake. Therefore, the earthquake causes residual deformation in the ground, resulting in kinematic forces that generate translations and rotations in the anchor pile. In [11], a simple and accurate method was presented to estimate the deformation of anchor piles caused by translation and rotation. Second, CDM cannot properly evaluate the subgrade reaction properties that greatly contribute to the bending deformation resistance of piles because it assumes that the anchor piles are embedded in horizontally stratified ground. Consequently, the bending deformation is poorly estimated [11]. Several studies have reported the subgrade reaction to piles in horizontally stratified [12-14] and sloping grounds [15-17]. Other studies have investigated the front ground of an independent pile installed behind a sheet pile wall [18]. However, the subgrade reaction characteristics of the anchor pile behind the sheet pile wall have not been reported.

This study aims to investigate the subgrade reaction properties of the ground in front of an anchor pile using Finite Element Analysis (FEA) to improve the accuracy in calculating the bending deformation of piles. At first, the Subgrade Reaction Modulus (SRM) obtained through the FEA was compared with that of the CDM. The difference between the subgrade reaction properties of the ground in front of the anchor pile and horizontally stratified ground was then clarified. Finally, it is shown that this difference increases with the increasing strength of a reference earthquake.

II. METHOD

This study considered two cross-sections at different water depths, -5.5 and -11.0 m [11], designed by the CDM, as shown in Figure 1. The elevation of the ground surface was 4.0 m. The anchor pile positions were 13.5 m and 18.9 m from the sheet pile wall, respectively. CDM considers the subgrade reaction under tension of the tie-rod and deformation of the pile. The bending moment generated in the pile was obtained by solving the following differential equation:

$$EI \frac{d^4u}{dy^4} = -Bp \tag{1}$$

where EI is the flexural rigidity of the pile, u is the lateral displacement of the pile at depth y , p is the subgrade reaction, and B is the pile width. The nonlinear load-displacement relationship of a pile often considers the nonlinear characteristics of the soil [19-21]. Based on the experimental results, the CDM calculates the subgrade reaction p as follows [5]:

$$p = k_c u^{0.5} \tag{2}$$

where k_c is the SRM. The SRM is often considered to depend on the foundation width [22-23], but this dependence is ignored when designing anchor piles [5].

Fig. 1. Profile of the sheet pile quay wall in this study. Values at a water depth of -5.5 m are given in parentheses and EL denotes elevation.

This study adopts the FEA code used in [11], namely the FLIP code [24], which is widely used to evaluate seismic responses of port facilities. Previous studies reported that the FLIP code accurately reproduces the residual deformation of the damaged sheet pile quay walls by earthquakes and the experimental results of the models [25-27]. The ground

conditions, structural members, boundary conditions between members and the ground, and earthquake ground motions were set to those in [11]. Viscos boundaries were applied to the bottom and side. A bilinear joint element was applied to the boundary between the wall and soil to consider wall friction. The interaction between the anchor pile and the ground was considered using the soil-spring element [28], which can take into account the three-dimensional effect. The stress-strain relationship of the ground is expressed by a nonlinear relationship based on the hyperbolic model [29] using the multispring element [30]. The hyperbolic model shows a substantial damping coefficient compared to the experimental result in the large shear strain range. Thus, the FLIP code modifies the hysteresis curve to reduce the area of the hysteresis loop compared to that given by the Masing rule [31] to prevent the damping coefficient from exceeding the maximum value [32]. Detailed equations for the hyperbolic model are given in [11]. The effects of liquefaction were neglected. Tables I and II show the ground conditions and dimensions of the structural members, respectively. The natural period of the ground was set to 0.8 s for both ground conditions, based on the values typically observed in the field.

TABLE I. GROUND CONDITIONS

Soil	ρ (t/m ³)	G_{ma} (kN/m ²)	σ'_{ma} (kN/m ²)	ϕ (°)
Backfill sand	2.0	58,300	89.8	38
Soil 1	2.0	72,200	198.5	39
Soil 2	2.0	125,000	279.2	39
Backfill stone	2.0	101,250	98	40
Wall friction angle (°)	In front of the wall: $\delta = 15$ Behind the wall: $\delta = 0$			
Common physical properties	$h_{max} = 0.24$, $K_w = 2,200,000$ kN/m ² $\nu = 0.33$			

Note: ρ = saturated unit weight, G_{ma} = reference shear modulus, σ'_{ma} = reference average effective confining stress, ϕ = shear resistance angle, h_{max} = maximum damping coefficient, K_w = bulk modulus of pore water, ν = Poisson's ratio.

TABLE II. DIMENSIONS OF THE STRUCTURAL MEMBERS

Water depth (m)	Sheet pile		Tie-rod	
	Depth of embedment (m)	Moment of inertia of area (m ⁴ /m)	Area (m ² /m)	Length (m)
-5.5	-11.8	0.000104	0.00063	13.5
-11.0	-20.1	0.000791	0.00128	18.9
Water depth (m)	Anchor pile			
	Pile length (m)	Moment of inertia of area (m ⁴ /m)		
-5.5	14.2	0.000304		
-11.0	12.5	0.000516		

Note: Elastic modulus of all structural members is 200 kN/mm²

As an example, Figure 2 shows a Finite Element (FE) mesh around the quay wall water depth of -5.5 m. The horizontal length of the FE model was 310 m. The height of the mesh was set at approximately 1.5 m to transmit seismic waves of up to 15 Hz. A two-step analysis was carried out. At first, a dead weight analysis was performed to evaluate the stress generated in the ground and structural members prior to the earthquake, and then a dynamic analysis was performed. Figure 3 shows the time history of the waveforms used in the calculations. The Hachinohe and Iwakuni waves have maximum accelerations of 1.0 and 1.5 m/s², respectively, and are dominated by low (0.4-1.5 Hz) and high frequencies (~4.0 Hz), respectively.

Fig. 2. FE mesh around the quay wall.

Fig. 3. Input ground motions: (a) Hachinohe wave and (b) Iwakuni wave.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Bending Deformation of the Anchor Pile

Figure 4 compares the CDM- and FEA-calculated bending moments of the anchor piles after the earthquake. In both results, the bending moment increases with depth because the distance from the tie-rod tension application point becomes longer. Then, the bending moment decreases at a certain depth, since the effect of the ground resistance becomes large. Here, the bending moment in the CDM calculation uses the residual tie-rod tension determined in the FEA. Except when the cross-section of a water depth of -11 m is subjected to the Hachinohe wave, the CDM gives larger bending moment maxima of the anchor pile than FEA. In the former exceptional case, CDM and FEA give very different generation altitudes of the bending moment maxima of the anchor pile. Figure 5 shows the bending deformation of the post-earthquake anchor pile obtained by doubly integrating the pile curvature. The deformation occurs in the negative direction, indicating that the anchor pile bends toward the side of the sea. In all cases, CDM predicted that the bending deformation begins increasing at elevations around -4.0 m, while FEA predicted a deeper onset of deformation increase, near -8.0 m elevation. In addition, except in the cross-section with the Hachinohe wave at a water depth of -11 m, the bending deformations obtained by FEA gradually decreased compared to CDM in the depth direction. In other words, the bending moments are smaller in FEA, and CDM overestimates the maximum bending moment of the anchor pile. In addition, when the Hachinohe wave was applied to the cross-section of a water depth of -11 m, the quay wall

deformation was highest and the bending deformation obtained by FEA was considerably large at the pile top. In this case, the bending deformation of the pile occurred from a deeper position in FEA than in CDM. Therefore, the altitude of the maximum bending moment of the anchor piles greatly differed between CDM and FEA.

Fig. 4. Bending moments of an anchor pile obtained by the CDM and FEA: (a) at water depth -5.5 m, (b) at water depth -11 m.

B. SRM in Front of the Anchor Pile

The SRM defines the ratio of the pile subgrade reaction to the bending deformation of the pile. The SRMs were calculated in a range over which the subgrade reaction and pile-bending deformation occur in opposite directions, and their distributions are shown in Figure 6. The SRM obtained by CDM can be obtained only below the tie-rod mounting height because the CDM regards the tie-rod mounting height as the ground surface. According to the Winkler foundation model, the passive failure line is generated at $l_m/3$ below the tie-rod mounting height, where l_m is the depth at which the bending moment of the anchor pile first becomes zero below the tie-rod mounting height.

Fig. 5. Displacement of an anchor pile obtained by the CDM and FEA for water depth of (a) -5.5 m, (b) -11 m.

The SRM obtained by FEA was larger at the highest altitude than at the tie-rod mounting height and was approximately constant below the tie-rod mounting height. Conversely, the SRM obtained by CDM decreased with increasing elevation because the CDM assumes a nonlinear relationship between the subgrade reaction and the bending deformation of the pile, as in (1). Thus, the increase in the subgrade reaction becomes subdued at high bending deformations of the pile. The distributions of the SRMs also differ between the methods. The CDM gives larger SRMs than FEA, especially when the Hachinohe wave is applied to the cross-section of the -11 m water depth.

Fig. 6. SRM distribution at water depth of (a) -5.5 m, (b) -11.0 m.

C. Causes of Differences in SRMs

To analyze the causes of the differences in SRM between the methods, the cross-section of the -5.5 m water depth was considered with only the self-weight and a static load, as shown in Figure 7. In Case 1, the tie-rod and anchor pile were removed, leaving only the cantilever sheet pile. In Case 2, the sheet pile and the tie-rod were removed while the front area of the sheet pile was reclaimed to simulate the horizontally stratified condition. After loading a self-weight, a concentrated load of 2.5 times the tie-rod tension was applied to the pile on the landfill side at the tie-rod mounting height. To elucidate the deformation mode of the ground, the concentrated load was determined through a self-weight analysis of the cross-section in Figure 1. Case 3 is similar to Case 2, but the self-weight and stiffness of the ground in the active failure region and the reclaimed area (gray area in the figure) were set to zero when applying the concentrated load to the pile. Case 4 is the condition illustrated in Figure 7(d).

Figure 8 shows the contours of the horizontal displacements. The dashed yellow line is the boundary at which the horizontal displacement changes dramatically. Hereafter, this boundary is referred to as the pseudo-failure line. The red dashed lines indicate the active failure line behind the sheet pile and the passive failure line in front of the pile assumed by the CDM. In Case 1, the pseudo-failure line and the active failure line obtained by the CDM were similar. The deformation mode of the ground behind the cantilever sheet pile roughly agreed with the CDM assumption. In Case 2, the pseudo-failure line was similar to the active failure line at the back of the pile, and the passive failure line at the front of the pile obtained by the CDM. The deformation mode of the pile front ground also approximated the CDM assumption under the horizontally stratified condition. Unlike in Case 2, the pseudo-failure line

occurring at the front of the pile in Case 3 was horizontal until it reached the active failure region behind the sheet pile. This difference was caused by the different self-weights and ground stiffnesses in the active failure region and the reclaimed area. Cases 2 and 3 presented different horizontal displacements at the pile head, -0.026 and -0.046 m, respectively, and different levels of pile deformation. The pseudo-failure line in Case 4 resembled a smooth coupling of the pseudo-failure lines of Cases 1 and 3. An active failure region was generated just behind the sheet pile, but the passive failure region assumed by the CDM was not generated at the front of the pile because the ground was not horizontally stratified and no subgrade reaction acted on the sheet pile above the seabed level. In particular, an enlarged active failure region occurred from the back of the sheet pile to the back of the pile.

Fig. 7. Study cases for analyzing the SRM differences between the CDM and FEA methods: (a) Case 1, (b) Case 2, (c) Case 3, (d) Case 4.

Fig. 8. Contour maps of horizontal displacements in the four cases: (a) Case 1, (b) Case 2, (c) Case 3, (d) Case 4.

The residual horizontal displacement contours were calculated for the cross-section of -11 m water depth to show the deformation mode during an earthquake (Figure 9). The red and purple dashed lines show the active and passive failure lines caused by the Monobe-Okabe seismic earth pressure [33]. The pseudo-failure (yellow dashed) line resembled that under self-weight action, the ground deformation mode during the earthquake was unchanged from that in the self-weight analysis. The pseudo-failure line was similar to the slip failure lines in [9, 34]. The FEA obtained a smaller SRM against the pile than CDM, because the pile front ground is not in a passive but in an expanded active state.

Fig. 9. Contour maps of residual horizontal displacements: (a) Hachinohe wave, (b) Iwakuni wave.

Fig. 10. Studied cases for analyzing the effect of ground height: (a) Case 1, (b) Case 2, (c) Case 3.

D. SRM Distributions

As described above, CDM assumes that the tie-rod mounting height is the ground surface although the subgrade reaction occurs above the tie-rod mounting height. Based on the cross-section of Case 2 (Figure 7), static analysis was performed for different heights of ground surface and the SRMs were compared among the cases. The concentrated load equaled the tie-rod tension obtained in the self-weight analysis. Figure 10 presents the studied cases. Case A is a basic case with constant weight and stiffness of the ground. In Case B, the weight and stiffness of the ground above the pile head (+2.4 m, gray area) were set to zero under a concentrated load. In Case C, the weight and stiffness of the ground above the concentrated load acting point (+1.4 m, gray area) were set to zero under a concentrated load. Case C accepts the CDM assumption.

Fig. 11. Bending deformation versus SRM: (a) Case A, (b) Case B, (c) Case C.

Figure 11 shows the SRMs and bending deformations of the piles. Similarly to the results of Figure 6, the SRMs in Cases A and B at the highest altitude exceeded those at the tie-rod mounting height. In Cases A and B, the bending deformations at the pile head were 0.0035 and 0.005 m, and the SRMs at the concentrated load acting heights were 20,000 and 15,000 kN/m², respectively. The large pile deformation and small SRM in Case B were attributed to the zero ground weight at altitudes above the pile head under the concentrated load application. The small ground stiffness was caused by the slight

confining pressure in front of the pile. Conversely, the SRM in Case C decreased with increasing depth, in agreement with CDM (Figure 6). The bending deformation at the pile head was much larger in Case C (0.03 m) than in the other cases. The SRM at the concentrated load action height was 1,600 kN/m², similar to that of CDM (Figure 6(a)). The SRM distributions differ between the two methods because CDM neglects the weight and stiffness of the ground above the concentrated load-acting height.

E. Maximum Subgrade Reaction

As shown above, CDM overestimated the SRM. However, the degree of overestimation varied with the conditions, being large in the cross-section at a water depth of -11 m subjected to Hachinohe waves. Figure 12 shows the hysteretic curves of the subgrade reaction obtained by FEA and the bending deformation of the pile through the cross-section of -11 m water depth before and after the earthquake. The subgrade reaction was linearly related to bending deformation at altitudes of -5.6 m for the Hachinohe wave and -2.2 m or deeper for the Iwakuni wave. The relationship was nonlinear and asymptotically approached the upper limit at altitudes higher than the above-mentioned. The tangential SRM was calculated by connecting the points along the straight lines to the origin. Before the earthquake, the SRM at +1.9 m altitude was 5,000 kN/m². After the earthquake, the SRMs were 500 and 2,500 kN/m² for the Hachinohe and Iwakuni waves, respectively. The SRM notably decreased after the earthquake because the subgrade reaction and bending deformation are non-linearly related. By comparing Figures 9 and 12, this nonlinear relationship is observed to occur in the expanded active failure region.

In CDM, the maximum value of the subgrade reaction is set as the passive earth pressure. Table III compares the maximum subgrade reactions and the passive seismic earth pressures based on the Monobe-Okabe theory. The maximum value of the subgrade reaction in the expanded active failure region was less than the passive earth pressure, indicating that the CDM overestimates the SRM when the subgrade reaction approaches the maximum value. The Hachinohe wave enhanced the seismic intensity through the cross-section of -11 m water depth. Thus, Hachinohe waves for this water depth cross-section severely deteriorated the ground stiffness, and the extent to which the subgrade reaction reached the maximum value became the widest. Therefore, the degree of overestimation of SRM by the CDM was larger in this scenario than in the other scenarios.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF PASSIVE EARTH PRESSURE AND MAXIMUM SUBGRADE REACTION

EL (m)	Passive earth pressure (kN/m ²)	Maximum subgrade reaction of FEA (kN/m ²)
+1.9	254	160
+1.0	316	200
-0.4	403	130
-2.2	515	120

Fig. 12. Relationship between subgrade reaction and bending deformation: (a) Hachinohe wave, (b) Iwakuni wave.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the subgrade reaction properties of anchor piles of sheet pile quay walls using FEA. The main conclusions of the current study are:

- The subgrade reaction against the anchor pile is smaller than that of the horizontally stratified ground because the sheet pile quay wall is irregularly shaped. CDM assumes a passive state in front of the pile and, hence, overestimates the maximum subgrade reaction acting on the pile.
- CDM ignores the effects of weight and stiffness of the ground at altitudes above the tie-rod mounting height, which non-negligibly contribute to the resistance of the pile. Consequently, the subgrade reaction in the range shallower than the tie-rod mounting height is greater than or equal to that in the deeper range.
- Under the effect of active ground failure, the upper limit of the subgrade reaction is lower in the ground in front of the anchor pile than in the horizontally stratified ground. This effect is enhanced with the strengthening of the seismic motions. It should be noted that this study investigated a limited number of examination cases. Therefore, further studies should be performed on various conditions, such as different anchor pile configurations and seismic motion intensities.

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